

Fibonacci Sequence Type Selfie Numbers with Factorial: Digit's Order

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Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, *basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers*, etc. These operations are applied for single variable. In two variables, we worked with *binomial coefficients type selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root*. This paper extends authors previous work for *Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers with factorial*. The work is up to 5-digits numbers.

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1 Introduction

Let's analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer's error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \tag{1}$$

Actually it is not a **printer's error**, it a represents number in its own digits. The first number similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

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(ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$\begin{aligned} 34425 &:= 3^4 \times 425 \\ 312325 &:= 31^2 \times 325 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \quad (3)$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

(iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! \\ 2 &:= 2! \\ 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\ 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\ 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\ 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\ 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\ 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!\end{aligned}$$

$$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$$

1.1 Fibonacci Sequence

Below are few examples of **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers** studied by author in previous work [22]:

$$\begin{aligned}235 &:= 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) \\256 &:= 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 &:= 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\4427 &:= (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 &:= F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 54128 &:= 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))\end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [22].

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

Selfie numbers with:

1. Basic Operations: [29];
2. Factorial: [26, 27];
3. Square-root: [14, 15, 35];
4. Factorial and Square-root: [14, 15, 16];
5. Fibonacci sequence: [23, 24];
6. Triangular numbers: [21, 32, 33];
7. Fibonacci and Triangular numbers: [24];
8. Binomial coefficients: [22];
9. Binomial coefficients: Fibonacci: [31];
10. Binomial coefficients: Triangular: [34];
11. S-gonal numbers: [17];
12. Centered Polygonal: [17];
13. Concatenation-Type: [28];
14. Quadratic numbers: [25];
15. Cubic numbers: [29];

The aim of this work is to bring **Fibonacci sequence type selfie numbers by use of factorial**. The work is in digit's order and is up to 5-digits.

2 Selfie Numbers With Fibonacci Values and Factorial: Digits' Order

This subsection brings **Fibonacci type selfie numbers** with basic operations. The results are in digit's order. The work is up to 5 digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and consecutive in blocks of 10. The second representations are for general values.

2.1 Two Digits Numbers

$$13 := F(1 + 3!)$$

$$21 := F(F((2 + 1)!))$$

$$23 := 2 + F(F(3!))$$

$$24 := F(2) \times 4!$$

$$42 := F(F((F(4)!)) \times 2$$

$$48 := (F(4))! \times 8$$

2.2 Two Digits Numbers

$$123 := F(12) - F(F(3!))$$

$$126 := (1 + 2)! \times F(F(6))$$

$$147 := 1 \times F(F((F(4)!)) \times 7$$

$$227 := -(F(2 + 2))! + F(F(7))$$

$$231 := -2 + F(F(3! + 1))$$

$$232 := -F(2) + F(F(3! + F(2)))$$

$$233 := F(F(2) + 3! + 3!)$$

$$247 := (-2 + F(F((F(4)!))) \times F(7)$$

$$248 := 2^{F(F(4)!)} - 8$$

$$254 := F(F(2 + 5)) + F(F((F(4)!))$$

$$257 := (-F(2) + 5)! + F(F(7))$$

$$264 := 2^{F(6)} + F((F(4)!))$$

$$273 := F(2) \times F(7) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$274 := F(2) + F(7) \times F(F((F(4)!))$$

$$315 := F(F(3!)) \times 15$$

$$335 := -F(F(3)) + (F(3!))!/5!$$

$$336 := F(3) \times F(3!) \times F(F(6))$$

$$347 := 3!!/F(F(4)) - F(7)$$

$$354 := (-F(3) + 5!) \times F(4)$$

$$362 := F(3) + 6!/2$$

$$363 := (3! + 6!)/F(3)$$

$$364 := (F(3!) + 6!)/F(F(4))$$

$$371 := -3! + F(F(7) + 1)$$

$$383 := 3! + F(8 + 3!)$$

$$384 := F(3) \times 8 \times 4!$$

$$420 := F(F((F(4)!)) \times 20$$

$$432 := F(4) \times F(3! \times 2)$$

$$433 := -F((F(4)!)) + F(F(3!))^{F(3)}$$

$$438 := -F(4) + F(F(3!)) \times F(8)$$

$$440 := F(F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} - 0!$$

$$441 := F(F((F(4)!))^{F(4-1)}$$

$$442 := F(F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} + F(2)$$

$$443 := F(F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} + F(3)$$

$$444 := F(F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} + F(4)$$

$$445 := F(F(4) + F((F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$447 := (F(4))!! - F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(7)$$

$$448 := F((F(4)!))!/((F(4)!)/8)$$

$$462 := F(F((F(4)!)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(2))$$

$$464 := -F(F(4))^{F(6)} + (F(4))!!$$

$$480 := 4! \times (F(8) - 0!)$$

$$483 := (F(F(4)) + F(8)) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$487 := (4!/8)!! - F(F(7))$$

$$496 := -F((F(4)!)) + 9!/6!$$

$$504 := F(F(5 + 0!)) \times 4!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 534 &:= F(5 + 3!) \times (F(4))! & 726 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 6 \\
 546 &:= (5 + F(F((F(4))!))) \times F(F(6)) & 727 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 7 \\
 564 &:= (5! + F(F(6))) \times 4 & 728 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 8 \\
 576 &:= -F(5 + 7) + 6! & 729 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 9 \\
 594 &:= -5! + F(9) \times F(F((F(4))!)) & & \\
 634 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 3!) + 4! & 732 &:= F(7) + 3!! - F(2) \\
 664 &:= -(F(6))!/6! + (F(4))!! & 733 &:= F(7) + (3 + 3)! \\
 679 &:= 6! - 7 - F(9) & 734 &:= 7 \times F(3) + (F(4))!! \\
 694 &:= 6! - F(9) + F((F(4))!) & 735 &:= 7 \times F(F(3!)) \times 5 \\
 706 &:= -F(7) - 0! + 6! & 746 &:= F(7) \times F(F(4)) + 6! \\
 707 &:= (7 - 0!)! - F(7) & 748 &:= 7 + (F(4))!! + F(8) \\
 714 &:= (7 - 1)! - (F(4))! & 754 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(-5 + F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 & & 775 &:= -F(F(7)) + 7!/5 \\
 720 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 0 & 842 &:= F(F(8))/F((F(4))! + F(2)) \\
 721 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 1 & 846 &:= F(8) \times (F(4))! + 6! \\
 722 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 2 & 945 &:= 9 \times F(F((F(4))!)) \times 5 \\
 723 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 3 & 947 &:= F(9) \times F(F((F(4))!)) + F(F(7)) \\
 724 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 4 & 953 &:= -F(9) + F(-5 + F(F(3!))) \\
 725 &:= (7 - F(2))! + 5 & 987 &:= F(9!/8! + 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Four Digits Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 1024 &:= (1 + 0!)^{2+F(F(4)!)} \\
 1035 &:= F(10) \times F(F(3!)) - 5! \\
 1045 &:= F(10) \times (4! - 5) \\
 1260 &:= F(F((1 + 2)!)) \times 60 \\
 1296 &:= F(12) \times 9!/(F(6))! \\
 1323 &:= (-1 + F(3!)^2) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 1324 &:= 1 + F(F(3!))^2 \times F(4) \\
 1336 &:= (-1 + F(3!) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(6) \\
 1343 &:= -1 + (F(3!))!/(4! + 3!) \\
 1344 &:= (1 + F(3! + 4)) \times 4! \\
 1345 &:= 1 + F(3)!/((F(4))! \times 5) \\
 1352 &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/5 - F(2) \\
 1353 &:= F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/(5 \times F(F(3!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1354 := F(-1 + F(F(3!)))/5 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$1359 := -1 + F(3!) \times 5 \times F(9)$$

$$1374 := (-1 - 3 + F(F(7))) \times (F(4))!$$

$$1376 := -1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(F(6))$$

$$1378 := 1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(8)$$

$$1398 := 1 \times 3! \times F(F(9) - F(8))$$

$$1404 := (1 + F(F((F(4))! + 0!))) \times (F(4))!$$

$$1427 := 1 \times (F(4))!! \times 2 - F(7)$$

$$1428 := F(1 + F((F(4))!)) \times 2 \times F(8)$$

$$1433 := -1 - (F(4))! + 3!! + 3!!$$

$$1434 := (1 - 4 + 3!!) \times F(F(4))$$

$$1435 := (-1 + F(4)) \times 3!! - 5$$

$$1436 := (1 - F(4)) \times (F(3) - 6!)$$

$$1438 := (1 - (F(4))!!) \times (3! - 8)$$

$$1439 := -1 + F(F(4)) \times (-3 + 9)!$$

$$1440 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 0$$

$$1441 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 1$$

$$1442 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 2$$

$$1443 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 3$$

$$1444 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 4$$

$$1445 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 5$$

$$1446 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 6$$

$$1447 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 7$$

$$1448 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 8$$

$$1449 := (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 9$$

$$1452 := (1 + (F(4))!! + 5) \times 2$$

$$1456 := F(1 + (F(4))!) \times (5! - F(6))$$

$$1457 := 1 + (-F((F(4))!) + 5!) \times F(7)$$

$$1462 := 1 + F(F((F(4))!)) + 6! \times 2$$

$$1463 := -1 + 4! + 6! \times F(3)$$

$$1464 := (-1 + F(4)) \times 6! + 4!$$

$$1467 := 1 + F(F(4)) \times (6! + F(7))$$

$$1470 := 1 \times F(F((F(4))!)) \times 70$$

$$\begin{aligned}1476 &:= (F(1 + (F(4))!) + F(F(7))) \times 6 \\1477 &:= 1 + (F(4))! \times (F(F(7)) + F(7)) \\1482 &:= (1 \times (F(4))!! + F(8)) \times 2 \\1483 &:= 1 + F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + 3!!) \\1484 &:= (1 + (F(4))!! + F(8)) \times F(F(4)) \\1493 &:= (-1 + F((F(4))!)/9)/3 \\1547 &:= (-1 + 5 \times 4!) \times F(7) \\1557 &:= -F(-1 + 5) + 5! \times F(7) \\1560 &:= 1 \times 5! \times F(F(6) - 0!) \\1561 &:= 1 + 5! \times F(6 + 1) \\1572 &:= (1 + 5!) \times F(7) - F(2) \\1574 &:= (1 + 5!) \times F(7) + F(F(F(4))) \\1575 &:= 15 + F(7) \times 5! \\1603 &:= F(16 + 0!) + 3! \\1631 &:= F(F(1 + 6)) \times (3! + 1) \\1637 &:= -1 + F(F(6)) \times 3! \times F(7) \\1638 &:= F(1 + 6) \times 3! \times F(8) \\1664 &:= -16 + (F(6))!/4! \\1674 &:= -1 \times 6 + 7!/F(4) \\1679 &:= -1 + (F(6))!/(F(7) - 9)! \\1686 &:= F(16) - F(8) + 6! \\1724 &:= -1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F((F(4))!))) \\1726 &:= 1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F(6))) \\1734 &:= 17^{F(3)} \times (F(4))! \\1745 &:= 1 + F(F(7)) \times F((F(4))!) - 5! \\1793 &:= 1 + (F(F(7)) - 9) \times F(3!) \\1823 &:= -1 + (F(F(8)) - 2)/3! \\1824 &:= (-1 + F(F(8)) - F(2))/(F(4))! \\1833 &:= (1 + F(F(8) - 3!)) \times 3 \\1843 &:= F(18) - (F(4))!! - F(F(3!)) \\1862 &:= F(18) - 6! - 2 \\1863 &:= F(18) - 6! - F(F(3)) \\1864 &:= F(18) - (6 - F(4))!! \\1873 &:= 1 + 8 \times F(F(7)) + F(3!) \\1886 &:= -F(1 + 8) + 8!/F(F(6))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1920 &:= (-1 + 9)! / F(F((2 + 0)!)) \\1943 &:= -(1) + (9 \times ((F(4))!^3)) \\1944 &:= (((1 \times 9)^{F(F(4))}) \times 4!) \\2016 &:= (F((2 + 0)!))! / (-1 + F(F(6))) \\2136 &:= (2 + 1) \times (3!! - F(6)) \\2145 &:= (2 + 1) \times ((F(4))!! - 5) \\2147 &:= (2 + 1)!! \times F(4) - F(7) \\2154 &:= (-2 + (1 + 5)!) \times F(4) \\2184 &:= ((2 + 1)!! + 8) \times F(4) \\2208 &:= F((2 + 2)!)/F(08) \\2214 &:= (F(22) + 1) / F((F(4))!) \\2274 &:= (2 + F(2 \times 7)) \times (F(4))! \\2304 &:= (2 \times (3 + 0)!)^{F(F(4))} \\2310 &:= 2 \times F(F(3!)) \times F(10) \\2312 &:= 2 \times (F(F(3!) + 1))^2 \\2317 &:= (2 \times 3)! + F(17) \\2330 &:= (2 + F(3!)) \times F(F(3! + 0!)) \\2353 &:= F(2) + F(F(3!)) \times (5! - F(3!)) \\2354 &:= 2 - F(F(3!)) \times (-5! + F((F(4))!)) \\2372 &:= 2 \times (3!! + F(F(7)) \times 2) \\2373 &:= ((2 + 3)! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) \\2375 &:= 2 + F(F(3!)) \times (-7 + 5!) \\2376 &:= (2^{3!} + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\2435 &:= (-F(F(F(2) + (F(4))!)) + 3!!) \times 5 \\2438 &:= -2 + 4 \times F(-3! + F(8)) \\2439 &:= -F(2) + 4 \times F(3! + 9) \\2444 &:= (F(2) + F((F(F((F(4))!)) - (F(4))!))) \times 4 \\2448 &:= F(2 \times (F(4))!) \times (-4 + F(8)) \\2449 &:= (F(2) + ((4! \times F(4)) \times F(9))) \\2456 &:= -F(2) + (-F(4) + 5!) \times F(F(6)) \\2458 &:= F(2) - (F(4) - 5!) \times F(8) \\2464 &:= -(F(2) + 4)! + F(-6 + 4!) \\2465 &:= F(2) + F(4! - 6) - 5! \\2474 &:= 2 \times F(4! - 7) - (F(4))!!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2478 &:= (-2 + (-F(F(4)) + 7)!) \times F(8) \\ 2518 &:= -2 + 5! \times 1 \times F(8) \\ 2519 &:= -F(2) + 5! \times F(-1 + 9) \\ 2533 &:= (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(3!)) - F(3!) \\ 2540 &:= (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F((F(4))!)) - 0! \\ 2541 &:= (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F((4 - 1)!)) \\ 2542 &:= (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F((F(4))!)) + F(2) \\ 2543 &:= 2 + (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times F(F(3!)) \\ 2544 &:= (2 + 5)! / F(F(4)) + 4! \\ 2545 &:= 25 + F(F((F(4))!)) \times 5! \\ 2561 &:= (2 + 5!) \times F(F(6)) - 1 \\ 2562 &:= (2 + 5!) \times F(6 + 2) \\ 2564 &:= (2 + 5!) \times F(F(6)) + F(F(4)) \\ 2574 &:= -2 + F(5 + F(7)) - F((F(4))!) \\ 2583 &:= -F(2) + F((-5 + 8) \times 3!) \\ 2634 &:= 2 \times (F(F(6)) + 3!^4) \\ 2637 &:= -2 + F(F(6) + 3!) \times 7 \\ 2638 &:= -2 + 6! + (F(3))! / F(8) \\ 2640 &:= (F(2) + F(F(6))) \times (4 + 0)! \\ 2644 &:= -2 + (F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))} \times (F(4))! \\ 2646 &:= F(2 + 6) \times (F(4))! \times F(F(6)) \\ 2647 &:= F(2) \times 6! \times 4 - F(F(7)) \\ 2648 &:= 2 + F(F(6)) \times (F(4))! \times F(8) \\ 2686 &:= -2 + (F(6))! / (F(8) - 6) \\ 2687 &:= -F(2) + (F(6))! / (8 + 7) \\ 2733 &:= -2^{F(7)} + F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(3!)) \\ 2735 &:= -F(2) - 7! + 3!^5 \\ 2747 &:= -2^{F(7)} + F(F(F((F(4))!))) - 7 \\ 2748 &:= -2^{F(7)} - (F(4))! + F(F(8)) \\ 2753 &:= F(F(2) \times F(7)) + 5! \times F(F(3!)) \\ 2795 &:= (-F(2) + 7! / 9) \times 5 \\ 2796 &:= 2 \times F(F(7)) \times (9 - 6)! \\ 2835 &:= (F(2) + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) \\ 2844 &:= (-F(2) - 8 + (F(4))!) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2846 &:= -F(F(2) + 8) + 4 \times 6! \\ 2856 &:= (2^8 - 5!) \times F(F(6)) \\ 2878 &:= -2 + 8! / (-7 + F(8)) \\ 2944 &:= F(2 \times 9) + (F(4))!! / F(F(4)) \\ 2946 &:= (2^9 - F(F((F(4)!))) \times 6 \\ 2964 &:= (F(-F(2) + 9) + 6!) \times 4 \\ 3016 &:= F(3!) \times F(0! + F(1 + 6)) \\ 3024 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F((0! + 2) \times 4) \\ 3029 &:= F(3! + 0!) \times F(F(-2 + 9)) \\ 3037 &:= F(3!) + F(0! + 3!) \times F(F(7)) \\ 3045 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (0! + 4! + 5!) \\ 3087 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (0 + F(8)) \times 7 \\ 3127 &:= (F(3!))! / 12 - F(F(7)) \\ 3150 &:= F(F(3!)) \times 150 \\ 3155 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(15)) \times 5 \\ 3159 &:= (3! - 1)^5 + F(9) \\ 3165 &:= F(F(F(3!)) - 1) - 6! \times 5 \\ 3173 &:= ((F(3) \times F(17)) - F(F(3!))) \\ 3176 &:= (3! + 1)! - F(F(7)) \times F(6) \\ 3240 &:= 3!! / 2 \times (F((F(4)!)) + 0!) \\ 3249 &:= (3!! + 2) / F(F(4)) \times 9 \\ 3257 &:= (3^2)! / 5! + F(F(7)) \\ 3264 &:= (F(3! \times 2) - F(6)) \times 4! \\ 3276 &:= 3! \times 2 \times F(7) \times F(F(6)) \\ 3296 &:= 3!! + F(2 \times 9) - F(6) \\ 3297 &:= 3!! + F(2 \times 9) - 7 \\ 3303 &:= F(3 \times 3!) - 0! + 3!! \\ 3304 &:= 3!! + F(3! \times F(04)) \\ 3312 &:= (F(3) + F(F(3!))) \times F(12) \\ 3325 &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 5 \\ 3328 &:= F(F(F(3)) + 3!) \times 2^8 \\ 3333 &:= 3! \times 3!! - F(F(3) \times F(3!)) \\ 3339 &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 9 \\ 3344 &:= F(3) \times ((F(3!))! / 4! - F((F(4)!))) \\ 3347 &:= (F(3!))! / (3 \times 4) - F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$3357 := (3!! - F(3)) \times 5 - F(F(7))$$

$$3359 := -F(F(3)) - 3!! + 5! \times F(9)$$

$$3360 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 0$$

$$3361 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 1$$

$$3362 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 2$$

$$3363 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 3$$

$$3364 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 4$$

$$3365 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 5$$

$$3366 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 6$$

$$3367 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 7$$

$$3368 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 8$$

$$3369 := (F(3!))! / (F(3) \times 6) + 9$$

$$3375 := 3 \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times 5$$

$$3376 := F(3!)^{-3+7} - 6!$$

$$3383 := F(3!) - (3! - F(8))^3$$

$$3384 := F(3!) - 3!! + 8^4$$

$$3386 := -3!! / F(3) \times F(8) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$3392 := F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 - F(2)$$

$$3393 := F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 \times F(F(3))$$

$$3394 := F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 + F(F(F(4)))$$

$$3396 := 3! \times (3!! - F(9)) - 6!$$

$$3427 := F(F(F(3!)) - 4) \times 2 + F(F(7))$$

$$3429 := (F(F(3!)) + (F(4))!! / 2) \times 9$$

$$3435 := -F(F(3!)) + 4! \times 3!! / 5$$

$$3437 := -3!! - 4! + F(3! + F(7))$$

$$3443 := (3 + 4)! - F(-4 + F(F(3!)))$$

$$3444 := (-F(3) + 4! \times 4!) \times (F(4))!$$

$$3447 := -F(F(F(3!)) - 4) + 4 + 7!$$

$$3448 := F(3 \times 4) \times 4! - 8$$

$$3451 := (F(F(3!)) + F((F(4))!)) \times (5! - 1)$$

$$3452 := -F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(4)) + 5!^2$$

$$3454 := -F(3) + (4! + 5!) \times 4!$$

$$3456 := 3 \times (4! + 5!) \times F(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3457 &:= F(F(3)) + 4! \times F(5 + 7) \\ 3460 &:= -(F(3!))! + 4 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - 0! \\ 3461 &:= -3!! + F(4! - 6 + 1) \\ 3462 &:= 3! + 4! \times F(6 \times 2) \\ 3463 &:= -3!! + F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)) - F(3)) \\ 3464 &:= F(3!) + 4! \times 6 \times 4! \\ 3466 &:= F(3) + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - (F(6))! \\ 3467 &:= -3!! + (F(4))! + F(6 + F(7)) \\ 3474 &:= -3!! + F(4) \times F(F(7)) \times (F(4))! \\ 3482 &:= F(F(3!)) - (F(4))!! + F(F(8) - 2) \\ 3483 &:= 3 \times ((F(4))!! + F(8)^{F(3)}) \\ 3485 &:= (3!! - F(F(4)) - F(8)) \times 5 \\ 3486 &:= F(3!)^4 - F(F(8) - 6) \\ 3487 &:= -F(3!) + (-(F(4))! + F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \\ 3492 &:= 3 \times (F((F(4))!) + F(9)^2) \\ 3497 &:= F(3) + (4! - 9) \times F(F(7)) \\ 3498 &:= F(F(F(3!))) \times 4 + F(9) - 8! \\ 3511 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(11) \\ 3525 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 25 \\ 3534 &:= (F(3 \times 5) - F(F(3!))) \times (F(4))! \\ 3535 &:= (3!! - F(5 + F(3))) \times 5 \\ 3536 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(3)^6 \\ 3537 &:= F(3) + 5 \times (3!! - F(7)) \\ 3538 &:= (F(3) + 5!) \times (F(3!) + F(8)) \\ 3544 &:= F(3!) \times 5! + F(F(4)) \times (F(4))! \\ 3545 &:= (3!! + 5 - (F(4))!) \times 5 \\ 3549 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (5! + 49) \\ 3554 &:= -F(F(3!)) + 5 \times (-5 + (F(4))!!) \\ 3563 &:= 3 - 5 \times (-6! + F(3!)) \\ 3564 &:= (-3! - 5! + 6!) \times (F(4))! \\ 3565 &:= (-F(3) - 5 + 6!) \times 5 \\ 3566 &:= 3! + 5 \times (6! - F(6)) \\ 3567 &:= F(3) + 5 \times (6! - 7) \\ 3568 &:= F(3!) + 5 \times (6! - 8) \\ 3569 &:= 3 + 5 \times 6! - F(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3573 &:= F(3!) + 5 \times (-7 + 3!!) \\ 3574 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(7) \times F(F(4)) \\ 3579 &:= 3!! \times 5 + F(7) - F(9) \\ 3580 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(8) + 0! \\ 3592 &:= 3!! \times 5 - 9 + F(2) \\ 3593 &:= 3!! \times 5 - 9 + F(3) \\ 3594 &:= -3! + 5! \times (F(9) - 4) \\ 3595 &:= (3!! - F(F(F(-5 + 9)))) \times 5 \\ 3597 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(-9 + F(7)) \\ 3598 &:= -F(3) + 5! \times (9 + F(8)) \\ 3605 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 5 \\ 3624 &:= 3!! \times (6 - F(2)) + 4! \\ 3627 &:= (3!! - (F(F(6)))^2) \times F(7) \\ 3638 &:= (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/3 - 8 \\ 3640 &:= (F(3!) + 6!) \times (4 + 0!) \\ 3643 &:= (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) - 3 \\ 3644 &:= (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) - F(F(4)) \\ 3646 &:= (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/(4!/F(6)) \\ 3647 &:= 3! \times F((F(F(6)) - (F(4))!)) - F(7) \\ 3648 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 8 \\ 3649 &:= (F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/(-(F(4))! + 9) \\ 3653 &:= 3^6 \times 5 + F(3!) \\ 3656 &:= (F(3!))!/6! + 5 \times 6! \\ 3658 &:= -F(3) + 6 \times F(5!/8) \\ \\ 3660 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 0 \\ 3661 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 1 \\ 3662 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 2 \\ 3663 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 3 \\ 3664 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 4 \\ 3665 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 5 \\ 3666 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 6 \\ 3667 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 7 \\ 3668 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 8 \\ 3669 &:= 3! \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3672 &:= 3! \times (F(F(6) + 7) + 2) \\ 3673 &:= 3!! + (F(F(F(6))) - 7!)/F(3) \\ 3674 &:= F(F(3!)) + (F(F(F(6))) + F(7))/F(4) \\ 3675 &:= (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 5 \\ 3684 &:= 3!! + (6! + F(8)) \times 4 \\ 3694 &:= -F(F(F(3!))) + F(6 + 9) \times 4! \\ 3696 &:= (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 6 \\ 3699 &:= (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 9 \\ 3705 &:= (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 5 \\ 3712 &:= F(3!) \times (F(F(7)) - 1) \times 2 \\ 3720 &:= F(3!) \times (F(F(7)) \times 2 - 0!) \\ 3724 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - 2) \times F(F(4)) \\ 3730 &:= F(3) \times (F(F(7)) \times F(3!) + 0!) \\ 3732 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2 \\ 3733 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) \times 3 - F(F(F(3!))) \\ 3734 &:= (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + 3) \times F(F(4)) \\ 3738 &:= 3! \times 7 \times F(3 + 8) \\ 3743 &:= F(F(F(3!))) - 7^4 \times 3 \\ 3744 &:= 3 \times F(7) \times 4 \times 4! \\ 3746 &:= -3!! \times (7 + F(4)) + F(F(F(6))) \\ 3749 &:= 3!! + F(7) \times F(4 + 9) \\ 3767 &:= 3! \times 7!/F(6) - F(7) \\ 3770 &:= (3 + 7) \times F(F(7) + 0!) \\ 3776 &:= (3! + F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\ 3827 &:= (F(3!))/F(8) \times 2 - F(7) \\ 3832 &:= -F(3!) + 8!/F(F(3!)) \times 2 \\ 3834 &:= ((F(3!))/F(8) - 3) \times F(F(4)) \\ 3835 &:= (F(3!))/F(8) \times F(3) - 5 \\ 3838 &:= -F(3) + 8! \times F(3)/F(8) \\ \\ 3840 &:= (F(3!))/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 0 \\ 3841 &:= (F(3!))/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 1 \\ 3842 &:= (F(3!))/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 2 \\ 3843 &:= (F(3!))/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3844 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 4 \\ 3845 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 5 \\ 3846 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 6 \\ 3847 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 7 \\ 3848 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 8 \\ 3849 &:= (F(3!))!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 9 \\ \\ 3856 &:= F(3)^8 + 5 \times 6! \\ 3857 &:= (F(3!) + F(8)) \times (5! + F(7)) \\ 3875 &:= (F(3!))!/8 - F(F(7)) \times 5 \\ 3882 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 2 \\ 3896 &:= -F(-3 + F(8)) + 9 \times 6! \\ 3927 &:= (F(3!) + 9) \times (-2 + F(F(7))) \\ 3935 &:= (3^9 - F(3!))/5 \\ 3945 &:= F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (-4 + 5!) \\ 3954 &:= 3! \times (F(9) + 5^4) \\ 3955 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times 5! - 5 \\ 3960 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times (6 - 0!)! \\ 3961 &:= (F(3!) + 9) \times F(F(6 + 1)) \\ 3963 &:= -3! + 9 \times (F(F(6)))^{F(3)} \\ 3967 &:= 3! + (9 + F(6)) \times F(F(7)) \\ 3968 &:= F(3!) \times (9!/6! - 8) \\ 3976 &:= F(3!) \times (9! - 7!)/6! \\ 4032 &:= F((F(4)!))!/(0! + 3^2) \\ 4048 &:= 4!!/(F(04) \times (F(8))!) \\ 4053 &:= ((F(4)! + 0!)! - F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \\ 4059 &:= -F(F((F(4)!)) \times 0! + 5! \times F(9)) \\ 4080 &:= (4 + 0!)! \times F(8 + 0!) \\ 4087 &:= -(F(4))!! + (-0! + 8)! - F(F(7)) \\ 4094 &:= -F(F(4)) + (0! - 9)^4 \\ 4128 &:= (F(4!) + (F((1 + 2)!)))/F(8) \\ 4147 &:= -F(F((F(4)!)) + 1) + F((F(4)! + F(7))) \\ 4157 &:= -4! + F(1 + 5 + F(7)) \\ 4160 &:= -F(F((F(4)!)) + F(-1 + F(F(6)) - 0!) \\ 4173 &:= F((4 - 1)! + F(7)) - F(3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4174 &:= -(F(4))! - 1 + F(F(7) + (F(4))!) \\4175 &:= -(F(4))! + F(1 + F(7) + 5) \\4179 &:= F(F((4 - 1)!)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \\4180 &:= F(-F(4 - 1) + F(8)) - 0! \\4181 &:= F((4 - 1)! + F(8 - 1)) \\4190 &:= F((F(4))!) + F(19) + 0! \\4193 &:= (F(4))! + F(19) + 3! \\4194 &:= ((F(4))!! - F(-1 + 9)) \times (F(4))! \\4196 &:= (F(4))! + F(19) - F(F(6)) \\4200 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) \times 200 \\4202 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) + F(20 - F(2)) \\4203 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) + 0! + F(F(3!)) \\4204 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) - 0! + 4! \\4205 &:= 4! + F(-2 + F(F(0! + 5))) \\4223 &:= 42 + F(-2 + F(F(3!))) \\4224 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 22 \times 4! \\4226 &:= -F((F(4))!)/(F(2 + 2))! + F(F(F(6))) \\4232 &:= F((F(4))!) \times 23^2 \\4236 &:= F(F((F(4))!) + 2) + F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) \\4237 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) + F(3!) \times 7 \\4239 &:= 4! + F(-2 + F(F(3!))) + F(9) \\4244 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) + F(4) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \\4245 &:= (F((F(4))!))^2 + F(4! - 5) \\4247 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(2) + F((F(4))!)) - F(F(7)) \\4249 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) + F(F(4)) \times F(9) \\4266 &:= (-(F(4))^2 + 6!) \times 6 \\4272 &:= 4! \times 2 \times F(F(7) - 2) \\4284 &:= F(F(4)^2) \times F(8) \times (F(4))! \\4293 &:= ((F(4))!! \times 2 - 9) \times 3 \\4302 &:= (-F(4) + 3!) \times (0! + 2)! \\4306 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! - 0!) - F(6) \\4307 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! - F(07) \\4310 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! - 10 \\4312 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! - (F(1 + 2))! \\4313 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! - 1 - 3!\end{aligned}$$

$$4314 := (F(4))! \times 3!! - 1 \times (F(4))!$$

$$4315 := (F(4))! \times 3!! - 1 \times 5$$

$$4318 := (F(4))! \times (3!! + 1) - 8$$

$$4319 := (F(4))! \times 3!! - 1^9$$

$$4320 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 0$$

$$4321 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 1$$

$$4322 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 2$$

$$4323 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 3$$

$$4324 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 4$$

$$4325 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 5$$

$$4326 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 6$$

$$4327 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 7$$

$$4328 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 8$$

$$4329 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 9$$

$$4331 := (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! - 1$$

$$4332 := (F(4))! \times (F(3) + (3 \times 2)!)$$

$$4333 := (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(3))$$

$$4334 := (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(4))$$

$$4335 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + 3 \times 5$$

$$4336 := 4^{F(3)} + 3! \times 6!$$

$$4337 := 4^{3!} + F(3!) + F(F(7))$$

$$4338 := (F(4) + 3!!) \times (-F(3) + 8)$$

$$4340 := F(F((F(4))!)) + 3!! \times (F(4))! - 0!$$

$$4341 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(F((4 - 1)!))$$

$$4342 := (F(4))! \times 3!! + 4! - 2$$

$$4343 := (4 + 3!!) \times (F(4))! - F(F(3))$$

$$4346 := F(F(4)) + 3! \times (4 + 6!)$$

$$4347 := F(4) \times 3!! + F(4)^7$$

$$4348 := ((F(4))! + 3!!) \times (F(4))! - 8$$

$$4350 := (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 0$$

$$4351 := (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 1$$

$$4352 := (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4353 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 3 \\ 4354 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 4 \\ 4355 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 5 \\ 4356 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 6 \\ 4357 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 7 \\ 4358 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 8 \\ 4359 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + 5) + 9 \\ \\ 4362 &:= (F(4))! \times (3^6 - 2) \\ 4364 &:= -4 + (F(3!) + 6!) \times (F(4))! \\ 4365 &:= (F(4))!! + 3^6 \times 5 \\ 4366 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times 6 - F(6) \\ 4367 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times 6 - 7 \\ 4368 &:= (4! + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(8) \\ 4373 &:= 4! \times F(3!) + F(F(7) + 3!) \\ 4374 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times (7 - 4)! \\ 4376 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! + 7 \times F(6) \\ 4378 &:= -F(4)^{F(3!)} - 7 + F(F(8)) \\ 4379 &:= -4 + (3!! - F(F(7))) \times 9 \\ 4383 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! + F(8) \times 3 \\ 4384 &:= (F(4))! \times 3!! + 8^{F(F(4))} \\ 4385 &:= -F(4)^{F(3!)} + F(F(F((8 - 5)!))) \\ 4386 &:= (F(4))! \times (3 + 8 + 6!) \\ 4394 &:= (-(F(4))!! + (F(3!))!)/9 - (F(4))! \\ 4395 &:= (-(F(4))!! + (F(3!))!)/9 - 5 \\ 4398 &:= (F(4))! \times (3!! + F(9) - F(8)) \\ 4399 &:= (-(F(4))!! + (F(3!))! - 9)/9 \\ 4410 &:= F(F((F(4))!))^{F(F(4))} \times 10 \\ 4414 &:= (F(4!)/F(F((F(4))!)) - 1) \times F(F(4)) \\ 4416 &:= 4! \times (4! - 1) \times F(6) \\ 4424 &:= F(4!)/F(F((F(4))!)) \times 2 + F((F(4))!) \\ 4428 &:= (F(4!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))) + 2)/8 \\ 4430 &:= -F((F(F((F(4))!)) - (F(4))!)) + (3! + 0)! \\ 4432 &:= (F((F(4))!) + F(4!)/F(F(3!))) \times 2 \\ 4434 &:= ((F(4))!! - F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) \times (F(4))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4437 &:= 4^4 + F(3! + F(7)) \\4438 &:= (F(4))! \times ((F(4))!! + F(F(3!))) - 8 \\4439 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(4) + 3!) \times 9 \\4440 &:= (F(4))! \times (F(4))!! + (4 + 0!)! \\4443 &:= (4! + (F(4))!!) \times (F(4))! - F(F(3!)) \\4444 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) + (F(4))!!) \times (F(4))! - F(F(4)) \\4446 &:= (F(4))! \times (F(4 + 4) + 6!) \\4447 &:= -F(F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F((F(4))!)) \times ((F(4))!! + F(7)) \\4448 &:= F(F(4)) + (F(4))! \times ((F(4))!! + F(8)) \\4450 &:= F(F(4) + F((F(4))!)) \times 50 \\4452 &:= -F(F((F(4))!)) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - F(F(5 + 2))) \\4459 &:= -F(F((F(4))!)) + (F(4) + 5)!/9 \\4462 &:= (F(4))! \times (4! + 6!) - 2 \\4463 &:= (F(4))! \times (4! + 6!) - F(F(3)) \\4466 &:= F(F(4)) + (4! + 6!) \times 6 \\4467 &:= (F(4))! \times (F(4))!! + F(F(6)) \times 7 \\4469 &:= -F(4) - F((F(4))!) + (F(6))!/9 \\4472 &:= -F((F(4))!) + (F((F(4))!))!/(7 + 2) \\4473 &:= 4^{F(4)!} + F(7 \times F(3)) \\4474 &:= F((F(4))!)/(-4 + F(7)) - (F(4))! \\4475 &:= F((F(4))!)/(-4 + F(7)) - 5 \\4476 &:= (F(4))! \times (F(F(4)) \times F(7) + 6!) \\4477 &:= -4! \times 4! + F(7) + 7! \\4479 &:= -F(F(F(4))) + F((F(4))!) \times 7!/9 \\4480 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 0 \\4481 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 1 \\4482 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 2 \\4483 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 3 \\4484 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 4 \\4485 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 5 \\4486 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 6 \\4487 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 7 \\4488 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 8 \\4489 &:= (F((F(4))!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4493 &:= (-F(4))!! + F(4) \times 9 + F(F(F(3!))) \\4494 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) \times (4! \times 9 - F(F(4))) \\4496 &:= F((F(4))!) + (F((F(4))!))!/9 + F(6) \\4497 &:= 4 + (F((F(4))!))!/9 + F(7) \\4498 &:= -F(4) + (F((F(4))!))!/9 + F(8) \\4536 &:= (F(4))! \times (5! + 3!) \times 6 \\4560 &:= -4 \times 5! + (F(6) - 0)! \\4563 &:= F(4)^5 + 6! \times 3! \\4567 &:= F((F(4))!) \times (-5! + 6!) - F(F(7)) \\4569 &:= F((F(4))! + 5) + (F(6))!/9 \\4574 &:= (F(F(4) + 5))! - F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)) \\4596 &:= -(F(4))! + 5! \times F(9) + 6! \\4599 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) \times (5! + 99) \\4634 &:= (F(-4 + F(F(6))) + 3!!) \times F(F(4)) \\4636 &:= (F(4!) - F(6)) / (F(3) + F(6)) \\4637 &:= -F(F(4))^{F(6)} + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) \\4644 &:= ((F(4))!! + (F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 4 \\4647 &:= (F((F(4))!) \times F(F(F(6)) - (F(4))!)) - F(F(7)) \\4656 &:= (F(4))! \times (6! + 56) \\4660 &:= -(F(F(F(4))) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(6) - 0!)) \\4663 &:= -F((F(4))! + F(6)) + (F(6))!/F(3!) \\4667 &:= 4 - F(F(6) + 6) + 7! \\4672 &:= -F((F(4))!) + 6! \times F(7)/2 \\4674 &:= -(F(4))! + 6! \times F(7)/F(F(4)) \\4687 &:= 4! - F(6 + 8) + 7! \\4688 &:= -4! + F(-6 + F(8)) \times 8 \\4689 &:= (F(4))!! + F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 9 \\4697 &:= -F((F(4))! + F(6)) + F(9) + 7! \\4704 &:= 4! \times (F(7) + 0!)^{F(F(4))} \\4725 &:= (-F((F(4))!) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(2) + 5)) \\4727 &:= -4! \times F(7) - F(2) + 7! \\4728 &:= -4! \times F(7) + (-F(2) + 8)! \\4733 &:= F((F(4))!) + (F(F(7)) - F(3!)) \times F(F(3!)) \\4735 &:= -(F(4))! + F(F(7)) + 3!! \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4736 &:= (-F(F(4))^7 + 3!!) \times F(6) \\4740 &:= (4 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!) \\4743 &:= (-4! + F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) \times F(F(3!)) \\4744 &:= ((F(4))!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 4 \\4745 &:= ((F(4))!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 5 \\4749 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(F(7)) - F(F(4) + 9) \\4753 &:= -(F(4))!! + F(F(F(7) - 5))/F(3) \\4763 &:= -4 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(F(3!)) \\4764 &:= (-(F(4))! + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6)) - F(4) \\4767 &:= (-F(4) \times F(7) + 6!) \times 7 \\4769 &:= F(F(F(4))) + 7! - F(6) \times F(9) \\4773 &:= -F((F(4) + F(7))) + 7! + 3!! \\4776 &:= 4! \times F(7) \times F(7) + 6! \\4778 &:= -F((F(4))!) - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(8) \\4779 &:= (F(4))! - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(9) \\4780 &:= ((F(4))! + F(F(7))) \times (F(8) - 0!) \\4783 &:= -4! - F(F(7)) + (F(8)/3)! \\4784 &:= F(4!) \times F(7)/(F(8) \times (F(4))!) \\4786 &:= -F(F((F(4))!)) + 7! - F(F(8) - F(6)) \\4787 &:= F(F(F(4))) - F(F(7)) - F(8) + 7! \\4789 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) + 7! - 8 \times F(9) \\4796 &:= -(F(4))! + 7 \times (-F(9) + 6!) \\4797 &:= -F(4)^7/9 + 7! \\4800 &:= (F(4))! \times 800 \\4807 &:= -F(4 + 8 + 0!) + 7! \\4827 &:= -4! + F(8) \times (-2 + F(F(7))) \\4837 &:= ((F(4))!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 7 \\4845 &:= -(F((F(4))!))/F(8) + F(4 \times 5) \\4848 &:= (F(4))!! + (8! + F(4!))/F(8) \\4856 &:= -4! + 8 \times F(5!/F(6)) \\4857 &:= -F(4) \times F(8) - 5! + 7! \\4859 &:= F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(8 + 5) - F(9) \\4863 &:= -F(-(F(4))! + F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))/F(3) \\4867 &:= F((F(4))!) \times F(F(8) - 6) - F(7) \\4869 &:= -4! + F(8) \times F(-(F(F(6)) - F(9)))\end{aligned}$$

$$4870 := -4! + F(8) \times F(F(7)) + 0!$$

$$4871 := -F((F(4))!) \times F(8) + 7! - 1$$

$$4874 := -F((F(4))!) \times F(8) + 7! + F(F(4))$$

$$4875 := -4! - F(8) + 7! - 5!$$

$$4877 := -4! + F(F(8) - 7) \times F(7)$$

$$4878 := (F(4))! + F(8) \times F(F(7)) - F(8)$$

$$4880 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 0$$

$$4881 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 1$$

$$4882 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 2$$

$$4883 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 3$$

$$4884 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 4$$

$$4885 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 5$$

$$4886 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 6$$

$$4887 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 7$$

$$4888 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 8$$

$$4889 := F(-(F(4))! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 9$$

$$4892 := F(4!) - 8! - F(9)^2$$

$$4897 := F(F(F(4))) - F(F(8) - 9) + 7!$$

$$4904 := -4 \times F(9) + (0! + (F(4))!)!$$

$$4914 := (F(4 + 9) + 1) \times F(F((F(4))!))$$

$$4917 := 4! + F(9 - 1) \times F(F(7))$$

$$4927 := -4! - F(9 + 2) + 7!$$

$$4934 := F(F((F(4))!)) + (F(9)/F(3))^{F(4)}$$

$$4937 := -F(4) \times F(9) - F(F(3)) + 7!$$

$$4938 := (-4! \times F(9) + (F(3))!)/8$$

$$4944 := ((F(4))! \times F(9) + F(F(4))) \times 4!$$

$$4947 := (F(4) - F(9)) \times F(4) + 7!$$

$$4957 := F(4) + F(9) - 5! + 7!$$

$$4960 := -(F(4))!/9 + (F(6) - 0)!$$

$$4967 := -F(F(F(4))) - 9 \times F(6) + 7!$$

$$4968 := -F((F(4))!) \times 9 + (F(6))!/8$$

$$4970 := (-F(F(4)) + 9)! - 70$$

$$4971 := -F(F(4)) \times F(9) + 7! - 1$$

$$4972 := F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + 7!/2)$$

$$4973 := -F(F(4)) \times F(9) + 7! + F(F(3))$$

$$4974 := (4! \times F(9) + F(7)) \times (F(4))!$$

$$4975 := F(-4! + F(9)) + 7! - 5!$$

$$4976 := -4! - F(9) + 7! - 6$$

$$4977 := -F(4) \times (F(9) - F(7)) + 7!$$

$$4978 := -(F(4))! \times 9 + 7! - 8$$

$$4979 := -F(4) \times 9 + 7! - F(9)$$

$$4982 := -4! - F(9) + (8 - F(2))!$$

$$4984 := F(F(F(4)) + 9) \times 8! / (F(4))!$$

$$4986 := -(F(4))! \times 9 + 8! / F(6)$$

$$4987 := F(F(4)) - F(9) - F(8) + 7!$$

$$4995 := (-F(F(4)) + 9)! - 9 \times 5$$

$$4997 := F(F(F(4))) \times (-9 - F(9) + 7!)$$

$$5027 := (5 + 02)! - F(7)$$

$$5032 := -F(5 + 0!) + (3! + F(2))!$$

$$5033 := -5 + (0! + 3!)! - F(3)$$

$$5035 := -5 + (F(03) + 5)!$$

$$5036 := -5 + 0! + (F(F(3)) + 6)!$$

$$5038 := -F(F(5 - 0!)) + (F(3!))! / 8$$

$$5039 := -(5 \times 0)! + (-F(3) + 9)!$$

$$5040 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 0$$

$$5041 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 1$$

$$5042 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 2$$

$$5043 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 3$$

$$5044 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 4$$

$$5045 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 5$$

$$5046 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 6$$

$$5047 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 7$$

$$5048 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 8$$

$$5049 := (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 9$$

$$5061 := F(F(5 + 0!)) + (6 + 1)!$$

$$5066 := 5 + (0! + 6)! + F(F(6))$$

$$\begin{aligned}5067 &:= 5 + 0! + F(F(6)) + 7! \\5069 &:= -5 + (0! + 6)! + F(9) \\5077 &:= 50 - F(7) + 7! \\5079 &:= 5 + 07! + F(9) \\5082 &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 2 \\5147 &:= 5! - F(1 + (F(4))!) + 7! \\5149 &:= -F(5 - 1) + F(4!)/9 \\5157 &:= -F(5 - 1) + 5! + 7! \\5186 &:= F(F(F(5 + 1))) - 8 \times 6! \\5187 &:= ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 7 \\5233 &:= -5! \times 2 + F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) \\5267 &:= F(F(5 + 2)) - 6 + 7! \\5272 &:= F(F(5 + 2)) + 7! - F(2) \\5273 &:= (5 + 2)! + F(7 + 3!) \\5274 &:= 5! \times 2 + 7! - (F(4))! \\5277 &:= 5 - F(2) + F(F(7)) + 7! \\5280 &:= 5! \times 2 \times (F(8) + 0!) \\5332 &:= -5! - F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(3!)))/2 \\5334 &:= (F(F(5 + F(3))) + F(F(3!))) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \\5336 &:= (-53 + 3!!) \times F(6) \\5337 &:= (5! - F(F(3!))) \times 3 + 7! \\5346 &:= (-5 \times 3!! + F(4!))/F(6) \\5353 &:= (5! + F(F(3 + 5)))/F(3) \\5367 &:= F(5!/3!) - 6 \times F(F(7)) \\5376 &:= (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 6 \\5384 &:= -F(5 + 3!) + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) \\5394 &:= (-5! + 3!!) \times 9 - (F(4))! \\5409 &:= (-5! + (F(4))!! + 0!) \times 9 \\5413 &:= (-5! + F(F(F((4 - 1)!))))/F(3) \\5417 &:= F(5 \times F(4) - 1) + 7! \\5433 &:= -5!/F(4) + F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) \\5434 &:= (-5! + F(F(F((F(4))!))))/F(3) + F(F((F(4))!)) \\5438 &:= (5! + F((F(4))!))^{F(3)} - F(F(8)) \\5443 &:= (-5!/F(F(4)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))/F(3) \\5444 &:= -5 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(F(4)) - 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5445 &:= (5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 45 \\5448 &:= 5! - (F(4))!! + F(4!) - 8! \\5462 &:= -5 - (F(4))! + F(F(F(6)))/2 \\5464 &:= 5! \times 4! + F(-6 + 4!) \\5471 &:= -5! + 4! \times F(F(7)) - 1 \\5472 &:= -5! + 4! \times F(F(7) \times F(2)) \\5474 &:= -5! + 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(F(4)) \\5484 &:= 5 + (F(4))! + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) \\5487 &:= (-5 + (F(4))!!) \times 8 - F(F(7)) \\5488 &:= (5! + 4 \times F(F(8)))/8 \\5533 &:= (5! + F(F(5 + 3)))/F(3) \\5535 &:= (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\5544 &:= (5! + 5! + 4!) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \\5589 &:= (5! \times 5 + F(8)) \times 9 \\5592 &:= 5!/5 \times F(F(9 - 2)) \\5593 &:= (5! + F(F(F((F(-5 + 9))!))))/F(3) \\5597 &:= 5 + (-5 + 9)! \times F(F(7)) \\5624 &:= -5! + (6! - 2) \times F((F(4))!) \\5632 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (3!! - F(2)) \\5634 &:= -5! + (F(6) \times 3!! - (F(4))!) \\5635 &:= -5! + F(6) \times 3!! - 5 \\5640 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 0 \\5641 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 1 \\5642 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 2 \\5643 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 3 \\5644 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 4 \\5645 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 5 \\5646 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 6 \\5647 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 7 \\5648 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 8 \\5649 &:= -5! + F(6) \times (F(4))!! + 9 \\5653 &:= 5! + (F(F(F(6))) + 5!)/F(3) \\5664 &:= -5! + F(6) \times 6! + 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$5673 := -F(5 + F(6)) - 7! + F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$5674 := F(5!/F(6)) + 7! + 4!$$

$$5693 := (5 + 6! - 9) \times F(3!)$$

$$5697 := 5 \times 6! + 9 \times F(F(7))$$

$$5733 := 5! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!)) + 3!!$$

$$5734 := -5 + 7! - F(F(3!)) + (F(4))!!$$

$$5736 := (-5 + F(7)) \times (-3 + 6!)$$

$$5738 := 5 + F(7) \times F(F(3!)) \times F(8)$$

$$5744 := (5 - 7 + (F(4))!!) \times F((F(4))!)$$

$$5747 := (-5 + F(7)) \times (F(4))!! - F(7)$$

$$5748 := -5 - 7 + (F(4))!! \times 8$$

$$5749 := -5 + 7! + F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(9)$$

$$5760 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 0$$

$$5761 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 1$$

$$5762 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 2$$

$$5763 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 3$$

$$5764 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 4$$

$$5765 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 5$$

$$5766 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 6$$

$$5767 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 7$$

$$5768 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 8$$

$$5769 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 9$$

$$5773 := -5! - F(7) - 7! + F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$5783 := -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) - 3$$

$$5784 := -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4))$$

$$5786 := 5 + 7! + F(8) + 6!$$

$$5796 := F((5 - F(-7 + 9))!)/F(6)$$

$$5833 := ((-5 + 8)!! + F(F(F(3!))))/F(3)$$

$$5864 := 5! + 8 \times (6! - F(F(4)))$$

$$5867 := 5! + 8 \times 6! - F(7)$$

$$5874 := 5! + 8!/7 - (F(4))!$$

$$5877 := -5 + F(F(8))/F(7) + 7!$$

$$5886 := (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 6$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5894 &:= -5! - 8! - F(9) + F(4!) \\ 5897 &:= F(F(F((-5 + 8)!))) - 9 - 7! \\ 5906 &:= -((F(-5 + 9))! + 0!)! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 5907 &:= F(F(F((F(-5 + 9)!))) + 0! - 7! \\ 5949 &:= (-59 + (F(4))!) \times 9 \\ 5973 &:= 5! \times 9 + F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!)) \\ 5994 &:= (5! - 9) \times 9 \times (F(4))! \\ 6027 &:= F(F(6) \times 02) + 7! \\ 6036 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 0!) - 3^6 \\ 6039 &:= -(F(6))! + F((0! + 3)!) - 9 \\ 6043 &:= -(F(6))! + 0! + F(4!) - 3! \\ 6044 &:= -6! - 0! + F(4! - 4) \\ 6045 &:= -6! + F(04 \times 5) \\ 6046 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 0!) + F(F(F(4))) - 6! \\ 6047 &:= -(F(6))! - 0! + F((-F(4) + 7)!) \\ 6048 &:= F(6 \times 04) - 8! \\ 6054 &:= -(F(6))! + 0! + 5 + F(4!) \\ 6056 &:= F(6) + F((-0! + 5)!) - (F(6))! \\ 6058 &:= F(F(F(6) - 0!)) \times (5 + F(8)) \\ 6066 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 0!) - 6! + F(F(6)) \\ 6074 &:= F(F(F(6))) + (0! - F(F(7))) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \\ 6084 &:= (6 \times F(-0! + 8))^{F(F(4))} \\ 6165 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 1) - 6! + 5! \\ 6174 &:= F(F(6)) \times (1 + F(7)) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \\ 6193 &:= 6! + F(F(-1 + 9))/F(3) \\ 6237 &:= F(F(6)) \times (2^{3!} + F(F(7))) \\ 6247 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times (F(4))!! - F(F(7)) \\ 6264 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times (6! - 4!) \\ 6324 &:= -F(F(6))^{F(3)} + F(-F(2) + F(F((F(4))!))) \\ 6333 &:= -(F(6))! - 3 + 3^{3!} \\ 6334 &:= -(F(6))! + 3^{3!} - F(F(4)) \\ 6336 &:= 6^{3!} - (F(3) + 6)! \\ 6338 &:= 6^{3!} + F(3) - 8! \\ 6343 &:= (F(6))!/3! - F((F(4))! + F(3!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6344 &:= -(F(6))! + F(3!) + (F(4))!^{F(4)!} \\6347 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))} - 7! \\6367 &:= ((F(6))! - 3!!)/6 - F(F(7)) \\6376 &:= 6! + F(3!) \times (-F(7) + 6!) \\6384 &:= F(F(6)) \times 38 \times F((F(4))!) \\6392 &:= -F(6) + (3!!/9)^2 \\6394 &:= -6 + (3!!/9)^{F(F(4))} \\6408 &:= (6! - F((F(4))!)) \times (0! + 8) \\6426 &:= (6! - (F(4))!) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \\6432 &:= (6! + 4!!/(F(F(3!)))!)/2 \\6433 &:= ((F(6))!/F(F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(3!))))/F(3) \\6435 &:= F(6 + 4) \times (-3 + 5!) \\6436 &:= F(F(F(6))) - F(4!)/3 + F(F(F(6))) \\6444 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4) \times F(4) \\6447 &:= (F(6))!/(F(4))! - F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(7) \\6448 &:= 6! + ((F(4))!! - 4) \times 8 \\6454 &:= -F(F(F(6))) + ((F(4))!! + 5) \times 4! \\6456 &:= 6^{F(4)!} + 5! - (F(6))! \\6459 &:= -F(F(6)) + (F(4))! \times 5! \times 9 \\6462 &:= (6 + F(4)) \times (6! - 2) \\6464 &:= (6! - F(F(4))) \times F(6) + (F(4))!! \\6466 &:= -(F(6))!/(F(4) + 6) + F(F(F(6))) \\6467 &:= (6 + F(4)) \times 6! - F(7) \\6469 &:= -F(6) - F(4) + 6! \times 9 \\6472 &:= F(6) \times ((F(4))!! + F(F(7) - 2)) \\6473 &:= F(6) \times (F(4))!! - 7 + 3!! \\6474 &:= 6! \times (-4 + F(7)) - (F(4))! \\6475 &:= 6! \times (-4 + F(7)) - 5 \\6477 &:= ((F(6))! - F(F((F(4))!)) + 7!)/7 \\ \\6480 &:= 6! + (F(4))!! \times 8 + 0 \\6481 &:= 6! + (F(4))!! \times 8 + 1 \\6482 &:= 6! + (F(4))!! \times 8 + 2 \\6483 &:= 6! + (F(4))!! \times 8 + 3 \\6484 &:= 6! + (F(4))!! \times 8 + 4\end{aligned}$$

$$6485 := 6! + (F(4))! \times 8 + 5$$

$$6486 := 6! + (F(4))! \times 8 + 6$$

$$6487 := 6! + (F(4))! \times 8 + 7$$

$$6488 := 6! + (F(4))! \times 8 + 8$$

$$6489 := 6! + (F(4))! \times 8 + 9$$

$$6490 := (6! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 9 + 0!$$

$$6493 := F(F(F(6))/F(4)) + 9 \times 3!!$$

$$6494 := (6! + F(F(4))) \times 9 - 4$$

$$6496 := -F(6) + 4! + 9 \times 6!$$

$$6497 := (6! - 4!) \times 9 + F(F(7))$$

$$6498 := (6! + F(F(4))) \times 9!/8!$$

$$6516 := 6! + F((5 - 1)!)/F(6)$$

$$6532 := -F(F(6) + 5) + F(F(F(3!))) - F(2)$$

$$6560 := (F(6) - 5)^{F(6)} - 0!$$

$$6569 := F(6 + 5) + 6! \times 9$$

$$6578 := -(F(6))!/5! \times F(7) + F(F(8))$$

$$6592 := -F(6) + 5! \times F(9 + F(2))$$

$$6594 := -6 + 5! \times F(F(9) - 4!)$$

$$6624 := -6! \times 6 - 2 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$6626 := -6! \times 6 + F(F(2 + 6))$$

$$6627 := (F(F(6)) + F((6 - 2)!))/7$$

$$6628 := -6! \times 6 + 2 + F(F(8))$$

$$6632 := F(F(F(6))) + 6 \times (-3!! + F(2))$$

$$6634 := F(F(F(6))) + F(6) - 3!! \times (F(4))!$$

$$6637 := (F((F(6) + (6 + 3))) + (7!))$$

$$6638 := 6 \times (-6! + F(3)) + F(F(8))$$

$$6642 := 6! + 6 \times F(4^2)$$

$$6644 := F(F(F(6))) + (-6! + F(4)) \times (F(4))!$$

$$6645 := -6!/6 + F(4 \times 5)$$

$$6647 := F(F(F(6))) + F(F(6)) + (F(4))! - 7!$$

$$6648 := 6! + (F(F(6)) + (F(4))!) \times 8$$

$$6656 := (6! - F(6) + 5!) \times F(6)$$

$$6660 := (F(6))!/6 - 60$$

$$6664 := -(F(6))!/6! + (F(6))!/(F(4))!$$

$$6677 := 6 + (6! + F(F(7))) \times 7$$

$$6679 := (F(6))! / 6 - 7 - F(9)$$

$$6684 := -6 \times 6 + 8! / (F(4))!$$

$$6693 := (F(6))! / 6 - 9 \times 3$$

$$6694 := (F(6))! / 6 - F(9) + F((F(4))!)$$

$$6696 := ((F(6))! - F(F(F(6)) - 9)) / 6$$

$$6707 := (F(6))! / (7 - 0!) - F(7)$$

$$6714 := (F(6))! / (7 - 1) - (F(4))!$$

$$6715 := (F(6))! / (7 - 1) - 5$$

$$6720 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 0$$

$$6721 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 1$$

$$6722 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 2$$

$$6723 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 3$$

$$6724 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 4$$

$$6725 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 5$$

$$6726 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 6$$

$$6727 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 7$$

$$6728 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 8$$

$$6729 := (F(6))! / (7 - F(2)) + 9$$

$$6731 := -F(F(6)) - F(7) + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)$$

$$6733 := ((F(6))! + F(7) \times 3!) / 3!$$

$$6734 := F(F(F(6))) / F(7) \times F(3!) - F(F(4))$$

$$6736 := -F(F(6)) + F(F(7)) \times (F(3!) + F(F(6)))$$

$$6744 := (6 + 7! / F(4)) \times 4$$

$$6747 := 6! + 7! + F(F(4) + F(7))$$

$$6760 := F(6) - F(7) + F(F(F(6)) - 0!)$$

$$6763 := 6 + F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(3!))$$

$$6770 := 6 + F(F(7) + 7) - 0!$$

$$6773 := F(6) + F(7 + 7 + 3!)$$

$$6776 := F(6) \times (7 + 7! / 6)$$

$$6780 := F(6) + 7 + F(F(8) - 0!)$$

$$6783 := (F(6))! - (F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 3$$

$$6813 := 6 \times 8 + F(-1 + F(F(3!)))$$

$$6833 := 68 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(3!)))$$

$$6834 := (6! + 8!)/3! - (F(4))!$$

$$6840 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 0$$

$$6841 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 1$$

$$6842 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 2$$

$$6843 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 3$$

$$6844 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 4$$

$$6845 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 5$$

$$6846 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 6$$

$$6847 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 7$$

$$6848 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 8$$

$$6849 := (6! + 8!)/(F(4))! + 9$$

$$6850 := F(F(F(6))) - 8^{5-0!}$$

$$6885 := F(-F(6)/8 + F(8)) + 5!$$

$$6914 := -(F(6))!/(9 + 1) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$6930 := 6 \times (F(9))^{F(3)} - 0!$$

$$6944 := F(6) + F(9)^{F(F(4))} \times (F(4))!$$

$$6967 := 6! \times 9 + 6! - F(F(7))$$

$$6984 := 6! \times 9 + F(8) \times 4!$$

$$7137 := 7! + (1 + F(3!)) \times F(F(7))$$

$$7142 := F(F(7) + 1) + F(F(F((F(4))!))) - F(2)$$

$$7203 := 7^{2+0!} \times F(F(3!))$$

$$7227 := 7! + F(2 + 2)^7$$

$$7231 := F(F(7)) \times 2 + F(F(F(3!))) - 1$$

$$7237 := (F(7) \times F(2))^3 + 7!$$

$$7246 := 7! - 2 + F(4!)/F(F(6))$$

$$7248 := 7! + F(24)/F(8)$$

$$7265 := (F(7) + 2 \times 6!) \times 5$$

$$7327 := 7! \times 3/2 - F(F(7))$$

$$7344 := 7! + (F(3) \times 4!)^{F(F(4))}$$

$$7346 := -7! + 3!! \times F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$7347 := (7! + F(F(3!)) + F(4!))/7$$

$$7349 := F(7)^3 + F(4!)/9$$

$$\begin{aligned}7350 &:= 7 \times F(F(3!)) \times 50 \\7353 &:= 7 + F(F(F(3!))) - 5 \times 3!! \\7357 &:= F(7)^3 + 5! + 7! \\7365 &:= -F(F(7)) \times 3 + (F(6))!/5 \\7366 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(F(3!))) \times (F(6) + F(F(6))) \\7413 &:= (F(F(7)) + (4 + 1)!) \times F(F(3!)) \\7433 &:= F(F(7)) + (4 + 3!) \times 3!! \\7434 &:= (7!/4 - F(F(3!))) \times (F(4))! \\7441 &:= 7^4 + ((F(4))! + 1)! \\7443 &:= (-F(7) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times F(4) + (F(3))! \\7444 &:= (F(F(7)) \times F((F(4))!) - F(4)) \times 4 \\7446 &:= F(F(7)) \times (F(4))! + F(4!) - (F(6))! \\7447 &:= 7^4 + (F(4))! + 7! \\7455 &:= 7! + F(F((F(4))!)) \times (5! - 5) \\7456 &:= F(F(7)) \times (-4! + 56) \\7464 &:= F(F(7)) \times (4! + F(6)) + F((F(4))!) \\7475 &:= 7! + ((F(4))!! - F(F(7))) \times 5 \\7488 &:= (F(7))!/((-F(4))!! + 8!) \times F(8) \\7491 &:= (F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) \times (F(9) - 1) \\7495 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(4)!/(F(9 - 5))! \\7497 &:= F(7) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \times 9 + 7! \\7547 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F((F(4))!)) - F(7) \\ \\7560 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 0 \\7561 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 1 \\7562 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 2 \\7563 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 3 \\7564 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 4 \\7565 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 5 \\7566 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 6 \\7567 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 7 \\7568 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 8 \\7569 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 9 \\ \\7584 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(8) + 4!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7616 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! - 1) \times F(6) \\7618 &:= 7! - 6 + F(18) \\7624 &:= 7! + F(-6 + 24) \\7632 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times 3!^2 \\7633 &:= (7! + F(F(F(6)))) - 3!! / F(3) \\7637 &:= F(7) + F(6 \times 3) + 7! \\7638 &:= (7! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3 - 8! \\7644 &:= F(7) \times F(F(6)) \times (4! + 4) \\7684 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(F(6)) \times F(8 + (F(4))!) \\7686 &:= 7! + F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 \\7688 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! + 8) \times 8 \\7694 &:= (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(9) - 4! \\7696 &:= (F(F(7)) + 6! + 9) \times F(6) \\7784 &:= 7! + (-7 + F(8))^{F(4)} \\7793 &:= F(F(7)) + 7! \times 9/3! \\7795 &:= -7 + F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 5! \\7831 &:= -F(F(7)) + 8! / (3! - 1) \\7854 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8) + 5!) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \\7855 &:= -F(F(7)) + (8! + 5!) / 5 \\7874 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8)) \times (7 + 4!) \\7904 &:= (F(7 + 9) + 0!) \times F((F(4))!) \\7913 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 1 - F(3!) \\7914 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - F((F(1 \times 4))!) \\ \\7930 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 0 \\7931 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 1 \\7932 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 2 \\7933 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 3 \\7934 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 4 \\7935 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 5 \\7936 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 6 \\7937 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 7 \\7938 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 8 \\7939 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$7942 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(F((F(4))!)) - F(2)$$

$$7943 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4! - 3$$

$$7944 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4! - F(F(4))$$

$$7954 := 7! + F(9) + 5! \times 4!$$

$$7994 := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 9 \times F((F(4))!)$$

$$8043 := 8! / (0! + 4) - F(F(3!))$$

$$8056 := 8! / 05 - F(6)$$

$$8063 := 8! / (-0! + 6) - F(F(3))$$

$$8085 := F(8) + 08! / 5$$

$$8092 := (8 - 0!) \times F(9)^2$$

$$8145 := 81 + (F((F(4))!))! / 5$$

$$8317 := 8! / 3! + F(17)$$

$$8344 := 8 \times 3!! + F(F(4)) \times (F(4))!$$

$$8354 := F(F(8)) - 3!^5 / F(4)$$

$$8364 := F(F(8)) + F(3) - F(-6 + 4!)$$

$$8373 := -F(8 \times F(3)) + F(7) \times 3!!$$

$$8426 := F(F(8)) - (F(4) + 2)! \times F(F(6))$$

$$8445 := 8! / 4! + F(4 \times 5)$$

$$8494 := -F(F(8)) + (F(4))!! \times 9 \times F(4)$$

$$8535 := (F(F(8)) - 5) + 3!! \times 5$$

$$8546 := F(F(8)) - 5!^{F(F(4))} / 6$$

$$8573 := F(F(8)) - (5! - 7) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$8642 := F(F(8)) - (F(6) \times (F(4))!)^2$$

$$8644 := (8 + 6! \times 4!) / F(F(4))$$

$$8684 := F(F(8)) - F(6 + 8) \times (F(4))!$$

$$8694 := F(8) \times 69 \times (F(4))!$$

$$8738 := F(F(8)) - F((7 - 3)!)/F(8)$$

$$8743 := F(F(8)) - F(7)^{F(4)} + 3!$$

$$8749 := F(F(8)) - F(7)^{-F(4)!+9}$$

$$8776 := 8 \times (F(7 + 7) + 6!)$$

$$8784 := 8! / (F(7) - 8) + (F(4))!!$$

$$8786 := F(F(8)) - (7! + 8!) / F(F(6))$$

$$8833 := (F(F(8)) + 8! / 3!) / F(3)$$

$$8856 := (F(8 + 8) + 5!) \times F(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}8932 &:= (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!) \times 2 \\8944 &:= (8!/9 - F((F(4))!)) \times F(F(4)) \\8947 &:= 8!/9 \times F(F(4)) - F(7) \\8974 &:= (8!/9 + 7) \times F(F(4)) \\9239 &:= F(9)^2 \times F(3!) - 9 \\9243 &:= -9 \times 2 + F(F((F(4))!))^3 \\9244 &:= F(9)^2 \times F((F(4))!) - 4 \\9284 &:= -9! + F(F(2) + 8) \times F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\9326 &:= -F(9) + F(3! + F(2)) \times 6! \\9333 &:= 9 \times F(3!) + F(F(3!))^3 \\9334 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times (3! - F(F(4))) \\9343 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) - (F(4))! + F(F(F(3!))) \\9345 &:= F(9 + F(3)) \times F(F((F(4))!)) \times 5 \\9346 &:= -(F(9) + 3!)^{F(F(4))} + F(F(F(6))) \\9347 &:= (-9 + 3! + F((F(4))!)) \times F(7) \\9349 &:= F(F(F(9 - 3))) - F(F((F(4))!)) + 9 \\9353 &:= (F(9 \times 3) - 5)/F(F(3!)) \\9354 &:= -F(F(9)/F(3)) + 5 + F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\ \\9360 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 0 \\9361 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 1 \\9362 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 2 \\9363 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 3 \\9364 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 4 \\9365 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 5 \\9366 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 6 \\9367 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 7 \\9368 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 8 \\9369 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 9 \\ \\9370 &:= 9 + 3!! \times F(7) + 0! \\9373 &:= F(9 - F(3)) + F(7) \times 3!! \\9394 &:= (F(9) + (3!! \times (9 + 4))) \\9407 &:= F(9) + ((F(4))!! + 0!) \times F(7) \\9434 &:= (-F(9 \times F(F(4)))) + F(3!)/4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9438 &:= (-F(9) - (F(4))!) \times F(3) + F(F(8)) \\
 9447 &:= 9 + ((F(4))! + (F(4))!) \times F(7) \\
 9450 &:= 9 \times F(F((F(4))!)) \times 50 \\
 9454 &:= F(9) \times ((F(4))! - 5!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 9464 &:= (9 + 4) \times (F(6) + (F(4))!) \\
 9486 &:= F(9) \times ((F(4))! - F(8) \times F(F(6))) \\
 9566 &:= -F(9) + 5 \times (F(6))! / F(F(6)) \\
 9576 &:= 9 \times (5! + F(7)) \times F(6) \\
 9633 &:= (F(9) - F(F(6))) \times (3!! + F(F(3!))) \\
 9645 &:= (9 + (F(6))! / F(F((F(4))!))) \times 5 \\
 9657 &:= 9 \times (6! + 5! + F(F(7))) \\
 9667 &:= F(9) + (6! + F(F(6))) \times F(7) \\
 9672 &:= (-F(9) \times 6 + 7!) \times 2 \\
 9724 &:= F(9) \times F(7) \times (-2 + 4!) \\
 9784 &:= -F(9) \times F(7) + F(F(8)) - (F(4))! \\
 9793 &:= -9 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 3!!) \\
 9847 &:= -F(F(9) - F(8)) + F(F(4)) \times 7! \\
 9864 &:= (F(9) + F(8 + 6)) \times 4! \\
 9873 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8) - 7) + 3!!) \\
 9938 &:= -(9! + 9!) / 3!! + F(F(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Five Digits Numbers

This subsection brings **5-digits selfie numbers**. Due to high quantity of number there are lot of extra brackets like "(...)". These can be removed by easily.

$$\begin{aligned}
 10037 &:= (-1 + (-((0! + 0!)) \times (F(F(3!)) - (7!)))) \\
 10038 &:= ((1 + 0!) \times (((0! + 3!))! - (F(8)))) \\
 10057 &:= (F((10 + 0!)) \times (5! - (7))) \\
 10064 &:= ((1 + 0!) \times (((0! + (6)))! - F((F(4))!))) \\
 10074 &:= ((1 + 0!) \times ((07)! - F(4))) \\
 10084 &:= (((-1 - 0!) - (-((0! - 8)))!) \times (-F(F(4)))) \\
 10134 &:= ((F(10) - 1) + ((F(3!))! / 4)) \\
 10138 &:= ((-101) \times F(3!)) + F(F(8)) \\
 10216 &:= ((-10) + F(21)) - 6! \\
 10223 &:= (((-1 - (((0! + 2))!))! - 2) + F(F(F(3!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 10224** := $((F(F((10 - 2))) - 2) - ((F(4))!))$
10225 := $((-1 - (((0! + 2))!)) + F(F(F((F(2) + (5))))))$
10226 := $(F(F((10 - 2))) - ((F(2) \times 6!))$
10227 := $((1 - (((0! + 2))!)) + F(F((F(2) + (7))))$
10228 := $-((((((1 + 02))!)) - 2) - F(F(8)))$
10233 := $((1 - (((0! + 2))!)) + F(F(F(3!))) + 3!$
10234 := $((F(F((10 - 2))) - 3!!) + F((F(4))!))$
10236 := $((10 + F(F(2^3))) - (6!))$
10238 := $((10 + 2) - 3!!) + F(F(8))$
10246 := $((10 \times 2) - ((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(6)))$
10248 := $((1 + F(F(((0! + 2))!))) - (((F(4))!)) - F(F(8)))$
10249 := $(-F(10)) + ((-2) \times F(4!)) / (-9)$
10283 := $((F(10) + 2) + F(F(8))) - 3!!$
10334 := $((-1 - 0!) + (F((3 \times 3!)) \times 4)$
10335 := $((-1 + F(F(F((03!)))) - F((3 \times 5)))$
10337 := $((1 + F(F(F((03!)))) - F((F(3) + F(7))))$
10338 := $((F(10) + F(F(3!))) \times (-F(3!))) + F(F(8))$
10344 := $((1 + 0!) + F((3! \times F(4)))) \times 4$
10345 := $((-1 + F(F(F((03!)))) - (((F(4))!)) - 5!))$
10346 := $((1 + ((0! + 3))!) \times (-4!)) + F(F(F(6)))$
10347 := $(F((10 + 3!)) - (((F(4))!)) \times (-F(7)))$
10356 := $((10 - 3!!) + 5!) + F(F(F(6)))$
10365 := $(F((10 \times F(3))) + (6! \times 5))$
10375 := $(F(10) + (F(3) \times (7! + 5!)))$
10393 := $((F(10) \times F(F(3!))) \times 9) - F(3)$
10433 := $((-1 - (F((F(04))!^3)) + F(F(F(3!))))$
10434 := $(F(F(F((10 - 4)))) - (F(3!)^{F(4)}))$
10436 := $((1 + 0!) - ((F((F(4))!))^3 - F(F(F(6))))$
10444 := $((1 + 0!) + F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(F((F(4))!)) \times 4!))$
10448 := $((-10) - ((F(4))!^4)) \times (-8)$
10449 := $((F(10) \times F(F((F(4))!))) + (F(4))! \times 9)$
10456 := $((-10) + (-4) \times 5!) + F(F(F(6)))$
10463 := $((1 - (04!)) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(F(3!)))$
10464 := $((1 - (-((0! - 4!)) \times F(F(6)))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
10466 := $((10 \times 4!) + F(F(F(6)))) - (6!)$

- 10473** := (((-10) × 4!) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(3!)))
10474 := (((1 + 0!) × (-F(4) - F(F(7)))) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
10478 := ((-1 - 0!) - ((F(F(4)) × F(F(7))) - F(F(8))))
10483 := (-1 + (((0! + F(F((F(4)!))) × (-F(8))) + F(F(F(3!))))))
10484 := (-1 + (F(F((0! + (F(4)!))) × (F(8) + 4!)))
10487 := ((1 + 0!) + ((4! + F(8)) × F(F(7))))
10506 := ((-F(10)) × F((5 + 0!))) + F(F(F(6)))
10546 := (((-10) × 5!) / F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))
10563 := ((-1 + (((-((0! - (5))))! × F(F(6)))) × F(F(3!)))
10567 := (((10 + 5) × 6!) - F(F(7)))
10568 := ((-1 - F(((0! + (5)) + F(6)))) + F(F(8)))
10570 := ((1 + F(F(F((0! + (5)))))) - (F((F(7) + 0!))))
10583 := (-1 - (((-((0! - (5))))! × (-F(8)^{F(3)})))
10584 := (F(F((1 + 05))) × (F(8) × 4!))
10592 := (1 - ((0! - 5!) × F((9 + 2))))
10606 := ((-10) × F((F(6) + 0!))) + F(F(F(6)))
10626 := (((1 + 0!) + F(F(6)))! / ((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))!)
10637 := (((-F(10)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3!))) - F(F(7)))
10643 := (1 + (((0! + F(F(6)))^{F(4)}) - 3!))
10646 := (((-10) × 6!) / 4!) + F(F(F(6)))
10647 := (-1 + ((0! + F(F(6)))⁻⁴⁺⁷))
10648 := ((1 + F(F(06)))^{4!/8})
10649 := (1 + ((0! + F(F(6)))^{-F(4)!+9}))
10658 := (((1 + 0!) × 6!) / (-5)) + F(F(8))
10664 := (((F(10) - F(6)) × (-6)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
10665 := ((F(10) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6)! / (-5!)))
10666 := (((F(10) × F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (6!))
10673 := (F(F(F((1 × 06)))) - (F(7) × F(F(3!))))
10674 := ((1 + F(F(F(06)))) - (F(7) × F(F((F(4)!))))
10678 := (((-1 - F((0! + F(6)))) - F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))
10684 := ((-(((1 + 0!)^{F(6)})) + F(F(8))) - (F(4)!))
10685 := ((-(((1 + 0!)^{F(6)})) + F(F(8))) - (5))
10690 := (-(((1 + 0!)^{F(6)})) + F(F((9 - 0!)))
10703 := ((-10) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F((03)!)))

- 10704 := (((-10) - F(F(7))) + 0!) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
 10712 := ((-1 - F(F(07))) + F(F(F(((1 + 2)!))))
 10714 := ((1 + F(F((0! + (7)))) - F(F((1 + (F(4)!))))
 10715 := (((1 + 0!) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F((1 + 5))))
 10716 := (((1 + 0!) - F(F(7))) + 1) + F(F(F(6)))
 10724 := (((10 - F(F(7))) + F(2)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
 10733 := (((-1 - F(F(07))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F(3!))))
 10734 := (((-1) × F(F(07))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + F(F((F(4)!)))
 10735 := (F(10) + (F((F(7) - F(3))) × 5!))
 10738 := (((-1 - 0!) × F(7)) × F(3!)) + F(F(8))
 10744 := ((-F(10)) + (F(F(7)) × (F(4)!)) × F((F(4)!))
 10746 := ((10 - (7!/4!)) + F(F(F(6))))
 10747 := ((F(((1 + 0!) + (7))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(F(7)))
 10749 := (((1 + 0!) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(9))
 10756 := ((-((10 × 7)) - 5!) + F(F(F(6))))
 10758 := (-(((F(10) + F(7)) + 5!)) + F(F(8))
 10769 := (((1 - F(-(0! - F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(9))
 10774 := (((1 + 0!) × (7! - F(7))) + ((F(4)!))!
 10784 := (((1 + 0!) × (7! - 8)) + ((F(4)!))!
 10786 := (((-1 + F((0! + (7)))) × (-8)) + F(F(F(6))))
 10793 := (-(((10 + 7) × 9)) + F(F(F(3!))))
 10794 := (((1 + 0!) × 7!) + (F(9) × F(F((F(4)!))))
 10802 := (-F((-1 + F(-(0! - 8)))) + F(F(F(((0! + 2)!))))
 10803 := ((1 - F((-0!) + F((8 - 0!)))) + F(F(F(3!)))
 10815 := ((-10) + F(F(8))) + (-1 - 5!)
 10816 := ((-10) + F(F(8))) - (-((1 - 6)!))
 10818 := (-(((1 + 0!)⁸⁻¹)) + F(F(8))
 10824 := ((10 + (F(8)²)) × 4!)
 10825 := (((-1 - 0!) + F(F(8))) + (F(2) - 5!))
 10826 := (F(F((1 × 08))) - (-((F(2) - (6))))!)
 10827 := ((1 + F(F(08))) - (-((2 - 7)!))
 10833 := ((F(10) + F(F(8))) - (F(3!) × F(F(3!))))
 10834 := ((-108) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 4
 10835 := (((1 + F(F(08))) + F(3!)) - 5!)
 10838 := ((-((10 + 8)) × 3!) + F(F(8)))

- 10843** := $((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (4! \times F(3)))$
10844 := $((-(108) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F(4))!)$
10845 := $((((-1 - 0!) + F(F(8))) + F(F((F(4))!))) - 5!)$
10846 := $(((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (4!)) - F(F(6)))$
10848 := $((-(((10)!/8!)) - F((F(4))!)) + F(F(8)))$
10849 := $(((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - F((F(4))!)) - F(9))$
10859 := $((-1 + F(F(08))) - (5! - F(9)))$
10863 := $((-(F((-10) + F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3!)$
10864 := $(((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) - (F(4))!)$
10866 := $((10 + F(F(8))) - (6!/F(6)))$
10870 := $((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - F((7 + 0!)))$
10872 := $(((-1 - 0!) + F(F(8))) - (72))$
10874 := $((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - (-7 + 4!))$
10885 := $((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - ((8 - 5))!)$
10888 := $((((1 + 0!) \times (-8) - F(8))) + F(F(8)))$
10889 := $(((-1 - 0!) + F(F(8))) - (F(8) + F(9)))$
10890 := $((-(F(10)) + F(F(8))) - ((9 \times 0))!)$
10897 := $(((-1 - 0!) + F(F(8))) - (F(9) + F(7)))$
10898 := $((-1 - F(-((0! - 8)))) + (-F(9) + F(F(8))))$
10902 := $((-(10) - F(9)) + F(F(F(((0! + 2))!))))$
10903 := $(((-(10) - F(9)) + 0!) + F(F(F(3!))))$
10904 := $(((-1 - 0!) \times F((9 - 0!))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
10912 := $((-1) \times F(09)) + F(F(F(((1 + 2))!)))$
10913 := $((1 + F(F(-((0! - 9)))))) - F((1 + F(3!)))$
10914 := $((((1 + 0!) - F(9)) + F(F(F((F((1 \times 4))!))))$
10922 := $(F((F(10) - F(9))) - ((2 + 2))!)$
10924 := $(F((F(10) - F(9))) - (-2 + 4!))$
10928 := $((((1 + 0!) \times (-9)) + F((F(2) \times F(8))))$
10929 := $((1 + F(F(-((0! - 9)))))) - (2 \times 9)$
10932 := $((-1 + F(F(-((0! - 9)))))) - F((3! + F(2)))$
10933 := $(F((F(10) - F(9))) - F((F(F(3)) + 3!))$
10935 := $(F((F(10) - F(9))) - ((3! + 5)))$
10938 := $(F((((1 + 0!) \times 9) + 3)) - 8)$

10940 := $F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 0$

$$10941 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 1$$

$$10942 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 2$$

$$10943 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 3$$

$$10944 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 4$$

$$10945 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 5$$

$$10946 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 6$$

$$10947 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 7$$

$$10948 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 8$$

$$10949 := F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(4)! + 9$$

$$10950 := (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (5 - 0!))$$

$$10952 := (F((F(10) - F(9))) + ((5 - 2)!))$$

$$10953 := (((-1 - 0!) + 9) + F(F((5 + 3))))$$

$$10955 := ((-1 + F(F(-(0! - 9)))) + (5 + 5))$$

$$10957 := (((1 + 0!) + 9) + F(F((-5) + F(7))))$$

$$10958 := (((-1 - 0!) + (9 + 5)) + F(F(8)))$$

$$10959 := ((-1 + F(F(-(0! - 9)))) + (5 + 9))$$

$$10960 := ((F(((-1 - 0!) + 9)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0!)$$

$$10963 := (((1 \times 09) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(3!))$$

$$10964 := (F((F(10) - F(9))) + (-6 + 4!))$$

$$10969 := ((((-1 - 0!) - 9) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(9))$$

$$10970 := ((-10) + F(9)) + F(F((7 + 0!)))$$

$$10973 := ((-1 + F(F(-(0! - 9)))) + (7 + F(F(3!))))$$

$$10978 := (((-1 - 0!) + F(9)) + F((F(7) + 8)))$$

$$10982 := (((1 + 0!) + F(9)) + F((F(8) \times F(2))))$$

$$10984 := ((((-1 - 0!) + F(9)) + F(F(8))) + (F(4)!))$$

$$10990 := ((10 + F(9)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))$$

$$10993 := ((F(((-1 - 0!) + 9)) + F(9)) + F(F(F(3!))))$$

$$10996 := (((1 + 0!) \times (F(9) - 9)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$10998 := (((1 + 0!) \times 9) + F(9)) + F(F(8))$$

$$11002 := ((1 + F(10)) + F(F(F(((0! + 2)!))))$$

$$11003 := (((1 + F(10)) + 0!) + F(F(F(3!))))$$

$$11032 := (((F(11) - 0!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 2)$$

$$11033 := ((F(11) - F(03)) + F(F(F(3!))))$$

$$11034 := ((F(11) - 0!) + F((-3) + 4!))$$

- 11036** := ((F(11) + 0!) + F(F((F(3) + (6))))))
11043 := ((F(11) + F((F(04)!)) + F(F(F(3!)))))
11044 := (((F(11) + 0!) + F((F(4)!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))))
11045 := (F(F(F(((1 + 1) + 0!)))) - ((F(F((F(4)!)) - 5!)))
11047 := (((F(11) - 0!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(7))
11054 := (((-11) - 0!) + 5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
11055 := ((-11) + F(F(F((0! + (5)))))) + 5!
11056 := ((-(1 × 10)) + 5!) + F(F(F(6)))
11058 := -((F(((1 + 1) + 0!))!) + (-5! - F(F(8))))
11064 := ((110 + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(4)!))
11065 := ((-1 + F(F(F((1 × 06)))))) + 5!
11066 := (((11 - 06))! + F(F(F(6))))
11068 := (((1 + 1) + (-((0! - (6))))!) + F(F(8)))
11073 := ((-1 + ((1 + 0!)⁷) + F(F(F(3!))))
11074 := (((1 + 1)⁰⁷ + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
11078 := ((-11) × (0! - F(7))) + F(F(8))
11084 := ((F((11 + 0!)) + F(F(8))) - (F(4)!))
11085 := ((F((11 + 0!)) + F(F(8))) - (5))
11090 := (F((11 + 0!)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))
11123 := ((-1 + (F(11) × 2)) + F(F(F(3!))))
11124 := ((F(11) × (1 × 2)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
11154 := (((-1 + F(11)) + 5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
11155 := ((F(11) + F(F(F((1 + 5)))))) + 5!
11156 := (((1 + F(11)) + 5!) + F(F(F(6))))
11173 := (F(F(F(((1 + 1) + 1)!))) + (F(F(7)) - 3!))
11184 := (((1 + 1) × F(F(-(1 - 8)))) × 4!)
11187 := ((F(((1 + 1) + 1)!)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(7))
11213 := ((F(11) × (2 + 1)) + F(F(F(3!))))
11214 := ((F(11) × 21) × (F(4)!))
11233 := ((-1 + (F(12) × F(3))) + F(F(F(3!))))
11234 := ((F((1 × 12)) × F(3)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
11305 := -(((F(11) + 3!) × (0! - 5!)))
11324 := ((F((1 + 13)) + F(2)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
11334 := ((11 + F(F(F(3!)))) + F((F(3!) + (F(4)!)))
11339 := (-1 + (((1 + F(3!))!)/(-F(3) - F(9))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 11342 &:= ((-F(11)) - (-((3!)!) \times F((F(4))!))) \times 2 \\
 11346 &:= (((-1 + F(F(((1 \times 3)!))))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11347 &:= ((F((11 + 3!)) + (4!)) \times 7) \\
 11366 &:= (((1 - F(F(((1 \times 3)!)))) \times (-F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11386 &:= ((F(((1 + 1) + F(3!))) \times 8) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 11388 &:= (1 + (((-1) \times F(F(3!))) \times (-F(8))) + F(F(8))) \\
 11417 &:= (((1 + 1) \times 4! + 1) \times F(F(7))) \\
 11433 &:= (-((F(11) - (4!^{F(3)}))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 11434 &:= (((1 - F(F((1 + (F(4))!)))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (((F(4))!)) \\
 11439 &:= (-1 + (((14)!/F(F(3!)))/9!)) \\
 11444 &:= (((F(11) - (F(4))!) \times (F(4))!) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 11445 &:= (((F(11) - F(4!)) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))/(-5)) \\
 11446 &:= (-1 + (((-1 + 4!)^{F(4)} - 6!)) \\
 11447 &:= (((-F(11)) \times F(F((F(4))!))) \times (-F(4))!) + F(F(7)) \\
 11448 &:= (-((1 + 1)) + ((F(F((F(4))!) \times 4! + F(F(8)))) \\
 11459 &:= (1 + ((1 - ((F((F(4))!)!)/(-5!)) \times F(9))) \\
 11463 &:= (((-F(11)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))/F(F(6)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 11465 &:= (((-11) - F(4!)) - F(F(F(6))))/(-5) \\
 11466 &:= (((1 + 1) + 4!) \times F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 11467 &:= (((F(11) \times (F(4))!) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(7)) \\
 11473 &:= (((F(11) \times (F(4))!) - 7) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 11478 &:= ((1 + 1) \times (((F(4))!)! + ((7! - F(8)))) \\
 \\
 11480 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 0 \\
 11481 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 1 \\
 11482 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 2 \\
 11483 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 3 \\
 11484 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 4 \\
 11485 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 5 \\
 11486 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 6 \\
 11487 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 7 \\
 11488 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 8 \\
 11489 &:= F(11) \times F(4)! + F(F(8)) + 9 \\
 \\
 11504 &:= ((1 + 15) \times (-0!) + ((F(4))!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 11523** := $((1 + ((-(1 - 5)))!^2)) + F(F(F(3!)))$
11534 := $(((-1 + F(15)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(F((F(4)!)))$
11536 := $((1 + ((1 + 5))!) \times F(3)) \times F(6)$
11545 := $(((-1 + F(F((1 + 5)))) + ((F(4)!))! - 5!$
11546 := $((1 + ((-(1 - 5)))!) \times 4!) + F(F(F(6)))$
11548 := $((F((1 \times 15)) - F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))$
11556 := $(F(F(F((1 \times 1) + 5))) + F((5!/F(6))))$
11563 := $(((-1 + F(15)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(3!))$
11564 := $((F((1 \times 15)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(4)!))$
11573 := $((11 \times 57) + F(F(F(3!)))$
11576 := $(F(F(F((1 \times 1) + 5))) + (7!/F(6)))$
11584 := $((11 \times 58) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))$
11594 := $((1 - F((-(1 - 5)))!) - 9)/(-4)$
11633 := $((1 - F((1 + F(6)))) + 3!!) + F(F(F(3!)))$
11634 := $(((-11) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3!))) + ((F(4)!))!$
11635 := $((F(11) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((3!)! - 5!))$
11640 := $((F(11) + F(6)) \times ((4 + 0!)!)$
11643 := $((1 + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + (-4!) + 3!))$
11644 := $((1 + 1) + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + ((F(4)!))!$
11649 := $((-11) + F(F(F(6))) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(9)))$
11653 := $((F(11) \times F(6)) - 5) + F(F(F(3!)))$
11658 := $((F(11) \times F((6!/5!))) + F(F(8)))$
11662 := $((-(1 + 1)) + F(F(F(6))) + (6! - 2))$
11663 := $(F(F((1 + 1) + 6)) + (6! - 3))$
11665 := $((-1 + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + (6 \times 5!))$
11666 := $(F(F((1 + ((1^6) + 6)))) + (6!))$
11667 := $((1 + ((1 \times 6))!) + F((F(6) + F(7))))$
11668 := $((1 + (1^6)) + 6!) + F(F(8))$
11673 := $((F(F((1 + 1) + 6)) + 7) + 3!)$
11674 := $((1 + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + 7) + ((F(4)!))!$
11676 := $-((F((1 + 1) + F(F(6))) + (-F(7) - (F(6)!)))$
11677 := $((F((1 + 16)) + 7!) + 7!)$
11678 := $((-1 + ((1 \times 6))!) + F(7)) + F(F(8))$
11683 := $((1 + 16) + F(F(8)) + 3!)$
11684 := $((-((F((1 + 1) + F(F(6))) - (F(8)))) + (F((F(4)!))!))$

- 11686** := (((-1 + F(F((1 × 6)))) + F(F(8))) + (6!))
11688 := (((-(1 + 1)) × 6!) - F(8)) × (-8))
11689 := (((-(11) + 6!) + F(F(8))) + F(9))
11693 := (((F(11) - (6)) × 9) + F(F(F(3!))))
11694 := (((1 + F(F((1 × 6)))) × F(9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
11698 := (((-(1 + 1)) + 6!) + F(9)) + F(F(8))
11716 := (-((F(11) - 7!)) + F((-1 + F(F(6))))
11734 := ((F(11) + (F(F(7)) × 3)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
11743 := (((11 × 7) + ((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(3!))))
11744 := (((-1 + F(17))/F(F(4))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
11748 := (-11) - ((F(7)⁴) - 8!))
11749 := (-11) + ((-7!) × F(F((F(4))!)))/(-9))
11764 := ((1 + 1) × ((-7!) + F(F(F(6)))) - (4!))
11768 := (((F(11) + F(7)) + 6!) + F(F(8))
11783 := ((117 + F(F(8))) + 3!!)
11785 := (((-1 + (-((1 - 7)))!) + F(F(8))) + 5!)
11786 := (((-((1 + 1) - 7)))! + F(F(8))) + (6!))
11794 := ((1 + 1) × (-((7! + 9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
11804 := ((-1 + F((-1 + F(8)))) + ((0! + (F(4))!))!))
11806 := ((1 + F((-1 + F(8)))) + ((0! + (6))!))
11807 := ((1 + F((-1 + F(8)))) + (0! + 7!))
11843 := (-F(-((1 - 18)))) + ((F((F(4))!))!/3))
11867 := ((((-1 + F(-((1 - 8))))!)/(F(6))!) - F(7))
11875 := ((F(11) + F(F(8))) + (7 × 5!))

11880 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 0
11881 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 1
11882 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 2
11883 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 3
11884 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 4
11885 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 5
11886 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 6
11887 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 7
11888 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 8
11889 := (-1 + F(-1 + 8))/8! + 9

- 11932** := $((-1 + F(F(-(1 - 9)))) + F((F(3!) \times 2)))$
11933 := $(F(F(-(1 \times 1 - 9))) + F((F(3) \times F(3!))))$
11936 := $((11)! / (F((9 - 3)))! + F(F(F(6))))$
11954 := $((-((1 + 1) - 9))! / 5 + F(F(F((F(4)!))))$
11996 := $((11 \times F(9)) \times F(9)) - 6!$
12098 := $(-((F(12) \times (0! - 9))) + F(F(8)))$
12136 := $(-F(((1 + 2)!)) + (((1 + 3)!)! / (F(F(6)))!))$
12137 := $(((((1 + 2) + 1)!)! / (F(F(3!)))!) - 7)$
12138 := $(-((1 + 2)! + (((1 + 3)!)! / (F(8)!))$
12142 := $(((((1 + 2) + 1)!)! / (F(F((F(4)!)))!) - 2)$
12143 := $(((-1) \times (21)! + (4)!)! / (F(F(3!)))!)$
12144 := $(((((1 + 2) + 1)!)! / (F((4 + 4)))!)$
12146 := $(1 + (((21)! + (4)!)! / (F(F(6)))!))$
12148 := $((1 + 2) + 1 + ((4)!)! / (F(8)!))$
12156 := $(12 + (((-((1 - 5)))!)! / (F(F(6)))!))$
12239 := $(-1 + (((F((2 + 2)))! \times (F(3!) + 9)))$
12243 := $((1 + ((F((2 + 2)))!^4)) + F(F(F(3!))))$
12244 := $(F(F(F(((1 + 2)!))) + (2 + ((F(4)!^4)))$
12245 := $(F((F(F(((1 + 2)!)) - 2)) + ((F((F(4)!))! / 5))$
12264 := $((-1 + (2^{F(2)+F(6)})) \times 4!)$
12265 := $(1 + (((((2 + 2)!)! / (F(F(6)))! + 5!))$
12266 := $((12)! / ((F(2) + F(6))!) + F(F(F(6))))$
12276 := $(((((1 + 2)!)! + F((2 + F(7)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
12336 := $((1 + (2^{F(3!)})) \times (3! \times F(6)))$
12337 := $(((-1 - (-2) \times F(F(F(3!)))) / 3 + (7!))$
12338 := $(((-1 + F(F((F(2) + 3!)))) \times 3! + F(F(8)))$
12343 := $((-1 + (F(F((F(2) + 3!)) \times (F(4)!)) + F(F(F(3!))))$
12344 := $(F(F(F(((1 + 2)!))) + (F(F((3 + 4))) \times (F(4)!))$
12347 := $(-1 + (((2 \times F(F(3!)))^{F(F(4))} \times 7))$
12357 := $((F(((1 + 2)!))! - (3 + (5! \times F(F(7))))$
12364 := $(((-1 + (2 \times (3)!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F((F(4)!)))$
12366 := $((1 - ((-2) \times (3)! + F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
12367 := $((12)! / (F(3)!)! - (-6! + F(F(7)))$
12369 := $(-((F(F(((1 + 2)!)) \times (F(F(3!) - F((6 + 9))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12372 &:= (F(F(F(((1+2)!)))) + (((3!)! - 7) \times 2)) \\
 12373 &:= (F(F(F(((1+2)!)))) + (((3!)! - F(7)) + 3!)) \\
 12374 &:= (-1 + (F((2 + F(3!))) \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(4)!)))) \\
 12375 &:= ((F(12) + F(F(3!))) \times 75) \\
 12376 &:= (((-1 + ((2 + 3)!) \times F(7)) \times F(6)) \\
 12377 &:= (1 + (((F(2) - 3!) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7)))) \\
 12378 &:= (-1 + (((2 \times (3!)! - 7) + F(F(8)))) \\
 12383 &:= (((-1) \times F(23)) + 8!) + 3! \\
 12385 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (3!)!)) + F(F(F(((8-5)!)))) \\
 12386 &:= (((((1 \times 2) \times 3)! + F(F(8))) + (6!)) \\
 12387 &:= (1 + ((2 \times (3!)! + F((8 + F(7))))) \\
 12393 &:= (((((1 + 2)^{3!}) \times F(9))/F(3)) \\
 12394 &:= ((-1 - ((-2) \times (3!)! - 9)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\
 12396 &:= ((1 - ((-2) \times (3!)! - 9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 12428 &:= (((F(F(((1+2)!)) + ((F(4)!!) \times 2) + F(F(8))) \\
 12432 &:= (((F(((1+2)!))! - (F(4!)/3))/2) \\
 12433 &:= ((-1 + (2 \times (4! + 3!))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 12434 &:= (F(F(F(((1+2)!)))) + ((4! + 3!) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 12444 &:= ((12 + ((F(4)!!) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - 4)) \\
 12453 &:= (((F(((1+2)!))!)/F(4)) - F((-5) + F(F(3!)))) \\
 12456 &:= (-F(12)) - (((F(4)!!) - 5!) \times (-F(F(6)))) \\
 12458 &:= ((12 \times ((F(4)! + 5!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 12464 &:= (F(F(F(((1+2)!)))) + (((4!)!/(F(F(6)))!)/F((F(4)!))) \\
 12467 &:= ((-1 + (((F(2) + (4)))! \times F(6))) \times F(7)) \\
 12474 &:= ((-1 + F((2 + F((F(4)!)))) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(4)))) \\
 12482 &:= (F(F(F(((1+2)!)))) + (4! \times (8^2))) \\
 12483 &:= ((-1 + (2^{-F(4)+F(8)}))/F(F(3!))) \\
 12503 &:= (-1 + ((F(25) - 0!)/3!)) \\
 12504 &:= ((-1 + F(25))/(F(04)!)) \\
 12506 &:= (F(F(F(((1+2)!)))) - (-5!) \times F((0! + (6)))) \\
 12523 &:= (F((1+2)! - 5!)^2 - F(F(3!)) \\
 12532 &:= (-12) + ((5! - F(3!))^2) \\
 12536 &:= (F((1+2)! - 5!)^{F(3)} - F(6)) \\
 12537 &:= (F(F(((1+2)!)) \times (F((5 \times 3)) - F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12540 &:= ((1 + 2) \times (F((-5) + 4!) - 0!)) \\
 12542 &:= (((1 + 2) \times F((-5) + 4!)) - F(2)) \\
 12544 &:= (((-12) + 5!) + (4))^{F(F(4))} \\
 12548 &:= (F(F(F(((1 + 2)!))) + (5 + F((-4) + F(8)))))) \\
 12549 &:= ((F(F(((1 + 2)!)) + 5!) \times F((F(F(4)) + 9))) \\
 12558 &:= ((-((1 \times 2)) - (5! \times (-5))) \times F(8)) \\
 12564 &:= ((12 \times F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + ((F(4))!)) \\
 12574 &:= (((-1 + F((2 \times 5))) \times F(F(7))) - F((F(4))!)) \\
 12576 &:= ((-1 + ((F(2) + 5!) \times F(7))) \times F(6)) \\
 12585 &:= ((-((1 + 2)) + (5! \times F(8))) \times 5) \\
 12587 &:= ((((((1 + 2)! - 5!) \times F(8)) - F(7)) \\
 12597 &:= (((F(((1 + 2)! \times 5!) + 9) \times F(7)) \\
 12600 &:= (F(F(((1 + 2)!)) \times 600) \\
 12626 &:= (((F(((1 + 2)!))! / ((6 - 2)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 12634 &:= ((F(((1 + 2)!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(3)!)/(-4!))) \\
 12647 &:= (F((1 + F((2 + 6)))) - (4! + 7!)) \\
 12653 &:= (F(F(F(((1 + 2)!))) + (F((F(F(6)) - (5))) + ((3)!))) \\
 12664 &:= (F(((1 + 2) \times 6)) + ((F(6)!/4)) \\
 \\
 12670 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 0 \\
 12671 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 1 \\
 12672 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 2 \\
 12673 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 3 \\
 12674 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 4 \\
 12675 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 5 \\
 12676 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 6 \\
 12677 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 7 \\
 12678 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 8 \\
 12679 &:= -1 + F(F(2) + F(F(6))) - 7! + 9 \\
 \\
 12684 &:= (F(F(((1 + 2)!)) \times (F((-6) + F(8))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 12732 &:= (((((1 + 2)! + ((F(7)! / ((3!)^2))) \\
 12733 &:= (-((((1 + 2)! - F(7))) + ((F(3)! / 3)) \\
 12738 &:= (F(F(F(((1 + 2)!))) + (7 \times (F(3)^8))) \\
 12744 &:= (F(((1 + 2)! \times (F((-7) + 4!) - 4))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 12747** := $(F(F(((1+2)!))) \times ((7!/(F(4)!) - F(F(7))))$
- 12754** := $(-(((1 \times 2) \times (7^5))) + F(4!))$
- 12768** := $(F(((1+2)!)) \times (76 \times F(8)))$
- 12783** := $(((-1 + F((2 + F(7)))) \times F(8)) - 3!)$
- 12784** := $((1 + F(((2+7) + 8))) \times F((F(4)!))$
- 12794** := $((F(((1 \times 2) \times 7)) \times F(9)) - 4!)$
- 12813** := $(((1+2) \times F((F(8) + 1))) - (F(3)!))$
- 12814** := $(-1 - (-F((2+8)) \times F((1 + (F(4)!))))$
- 12818** := $(F((((1+2)! + 8)) \times F((1+8)))$
- 12830** := $(-1 + (F((2 \times 8)) \times F((3! + 0!)))$
- 12831** := $(F(((1 \times 2) \times 8)) \times F((3! + 1)))$
- 12832** := $(1 + (F((2 \times 8)) \times F((3! + F(2))))$
- 12834** := $(((1+2)! \times (-F(8) + ((3!) \times F(4))))$
- 12836** := $(((((((1+2)!))! \times F(8))/F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
- 12837** := $(((1+2)! + (F((8 \times F(3))) \times F(7)))$
- 12839** := $(F(F(((1+2)!)) - (F((8+3!)) \times (-F(9))))$
- 12843** := $(((((((1+2)!))! - F(8)) - (-((4!)!/(F(F(3)!))!))$
- 12863** := $((((F(((1+2)!))!)/F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 3)$
- 12864** := $((((F(((1+2)!))!)/F(8)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(4)))$
- 12866** := $(F(F(((1^2) \times 8))) + ((F(6)!)/F(F(6))))$
- 12868** := $((1 \times 2) - ((-8!)/F(F(6))) - F(F(8)))$
- 12870** := $(F(((1 \times 2) + 8)) \times (F(F(7)) + 0!))$
- 12873** := $(F(F(((1+2)!)) \times (F((8+7)) + 3))$
- 12874** := $(F(F(F(((1+2)!))) + ((8 + F(F(7))) \times F((F(4)!)))$
- 12879** := $(-1 - (((-2) - F(8)) \times 7!)/9)$
- 12924** := $(((1 \times 2) \times 9) \times (-2 + ((F(4)!))!))$
- 12932** := $((((F(((1+2)!))!)/(-9)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 2)$
- 12936** := $((((1+2)! + F((9+3!))) \times F(F(6)))$
- 12938** := $(-1 + (((2 \times 9) \times (3!)! - F(8)))$
- 12939** := $-((F(F(((1+2)!)) + (9!/(3! - F(9))))$
- 12941** := $(-1 + ((2 \times 9) \times (((F(4)!))! - 1)))$
- 12942** := $(((1 \times 2) \times 9) \times (((F(4)!))! - F(2)))$
- 12943** := $(1 + ((2 \times 9) \times (((F(4)!))! - F(F(3))))$
- 12944** := $((F(F(((1+2)!)) + F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) \times F((F(4)!))$
- 12947** := $(((((((1+2)!))! \times 9) \times F(F(4))) - F(7))$

- 12954** := $((-1 + ((2 \times 9) \times 5!)) \times (F(4))!)$
12957 := $((F(F(((1 + 2))!)) \times F((9 + 5))) + (7!))$
12974 := $(((((1 + 2))! \times 9) + 7) \times F(F(4)))$
12979 := $(-F((1 + (2 \times 9)))) - ((F(7))!/(-9!))$
12986 := $(((((12)!/9!) + F(F(8))) + (6!))$
13043 := $((-F(13)) \times (-0! - F((F(4))!))) + F(F(F(3!)))$
13047 := $(-1 - (F(3!) \times ((-0! - (F(4))!) \times F(F(7))))$
13048 := $(-F(13)) \times ((0! + (F(4))!) \times (-8))$
13063 := $-((F((13 + 0!)) - ((F(6))!/3))$
13064 := $((F(13) - F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-F(F(4))))$
13122 := $((1 \times 3)^{F((1+2)!)} \times 2)$
13123 := $(1 - (3^{F((1+2)!)} \times (-F(3))))$
13124 := $((1 + (3^{F((1+2)!)})) \times F(F(4)))$
13133 := $((1 \times 3)^{1+3!} + F(F(F(3!))))$
13134 := $((1 - F(F(F(3!))))/(1 - 3!) \times (F(4))!)$
13135 := $(1 + (((F(F(F(3!))) - 1) \times 3!)/5))$
13143 := $(F(F(F(((1 \times 3))!))) + (F((1 + (F(4))!))³))$
13144 := $((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F((1 + (F(4))!))^{F(4)}))$
13146 := $((1 + ((3! - 1)⁴)) \times F(F(6)))$
13153 := $((-1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F((-((1 - 5)))!)/F(F(3!))))$
13154 := $(F(F(F(((1 \times 3))!))) - (-F((-((1 - 5)))!)/F(F((F(4))!))))$
13183 := $(1 + (3! \times (F(-((1 - 8)))³)))$
13186 := $(((-1) \times (F(3))!)/(-18) + F(F(F(6))))$
13195 := $((1 + F((F(3!) + 1))) \times F((9 + 5)))$
13207 := $(((-1) \times (F(3))!)/(-2 - 0!) - F(F(7)))$
13230 := $((F(F(((1 \times 3))!))²) \times 30)$
13232 := $((1 + 3!)! + (2^{F(3!+F(2))}))$
13235 := $((1 - ((F(F(3!))²) \times (-3!))) \times 5)$
13242 := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - F((2 \times (F(4))!))) \times 2)$
13243 := $(1 - (3! \times (F(2) - (F(4)!/F(F(3!)))))$
13248 := $((1 \times 3)! \times F(24)/F(8))$
13249 := $((-1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((2^{F(F(4)!)} \times 9))$
13263 := $((1 \times 3) \times F((-2) + F(F(6)))) + ((3!)!)$
13264 := $(1 + (3 \times F((-2) + F(F(6)))) + ((F(4))!))$

- 13273** := $(1 + (F(F(3!)) \times (2 + (7!/F(3!)))))$
13274 := $((F((1 + (F(3!) \times 2))) + (7!)) \times F(F(4)))$
13275 := $((-1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((-2) \times F(F(7))) \times (-5))$
13284 := $(((-1 - F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))))/(-8)) \times (F(4)!)$
13297 := $(F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!))) + (F((2 \times 9)) - F(F(7))))$
13320 := $(-(((1 + 3)!)) - ((F(3!))!/(-2 - 0!))$
13326 := $((1 \times 3)^{F(3!)} + F((-F(2) + F(F(6))))$
13329 := $((-1 + (((3!)! + F(F(3!))) \times 2)) \times 9$
13334 := $(F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + ((3^{F(3!)} + F((F(4)!)))$
13335 := $(((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-3)) - (F(F(3!)) \times 5)$
13337 := $(((((1 + 3)!)^3 - 3!!) + F(F(7)))$
13338 := $((1 \times 3) \times 3!) \times ((3!)! + (F(8)))$
13339 := $(1 - (((3!)! + F(F(3!))) \times (F(3) \times (-9)))$
13343 := $(F((1 + F(F(3!)))) - ((-((3!)! - F((F(4)!)) \times (-3!)))$
13344 := $(((((1 + 3)!)! \times (3!)! - F(4!))/F(4))$
13345 := $(1 + (((F(3!))!/3) + ((4! - 5!)))$
13346 := $(((((1 + 3)!)!^{F(3)})/F(4)! + F(F(F(6))))$
13348 := $(1 + (((F(F(3)) + 3!)^4) + F(F(8))))$
13352 := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - F((3! + (5)))) \times 2$
13354 := $((1 + F(F(3!))) \times (F((3 \times 5)) - F(4)))$
13359 := $(F((1 + F(F(3!)))) + ((F(3!) + 5!) \times (-F(9)))$
13362 := $(((((1 + 3)!)! + (3^{F(6)})) \times 2$
13363 := $((-(F(13) - F(3))) + (F(6)!)/3$
13365 := $(F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - (F((F(3) + F(6))) \times (-5!))$
13369 := $(1 + (((F(3!))!/3) - (F(6) \times 9)))$
13370 := $(((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-3)) - (70))$
13374 := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - ((3! \times F(7)))) \times F(F(4)))$
13375 := $-(((1 + 3)!)^3 \times (F(7) - 5!))$
13376 := $(((((1 + 3)!) + 3!!) + F(F(7))) \times F(6))$
13377 := $((-1 + (F(3!) \times (3! + F(F(7)))) \times 7$
13383 := $(((((1 + 3)!)^3) - (F(8)^{F(3)}))$
13384 := $(((-1 - 3!) \times F(3!)) + (8!/F(4)))$
13386 := $((1 + 3) \times F(-(3! - F(8)))) + F(F(F(6)))$
13387 := $((-1 + (F(3!)!)) + ((-F(3)) \times F(F(8))) - (7!))$

- 13388** := $-((((1 + 3!)! - ((-F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + 8!))$
13393 := $(1 + (F((F(3) \times 3!)) \times 93))$
13394 := $(F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!))) + ((3 \times F(9)) \times 4!))$
13395 := $((((-1 + 3!)! + F(F(3!))) \times 95)$
13397 := $((((1 - 3!!) \times 3!) + F((9 + F(7))))$
13398 := $((((-1 + 3!!) - 3) \times F(9)) - F(F(8)))$
13406 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - F((0! + F(6))))$
13414 := $(-1 + (((F(3!)!)/F(4)) - (1 + 4!)))$
13415 := $(-1 + (((F(3!)!)/F(4)) - (-((1 - 5)!)))$
13418 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - (1 + F(8)))$
13419 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - F(-((1 - 9))))$
13420 := $((1 + F(F(3!))) \times F((4^2 - 0!)))$
13423 := $(-1 + (((F(3!)!)/F(4)) - (2 \times F(3!))))$
13424 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - (2^4))$
13425 := $((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-2 + 5!)))$
13426 := $(-1 + (((F(3!)!)/F(4)) - F((F(2) + (6))))$
13427 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - (F(2) \times F(7)))$
13428 := $(1 + (((F(3!)!)/F(4)) - F(-((F(2) - 8))))$
13429 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - (2 + 9))$
13430 := $(-1 + (((F(3!)!)/F(4)) - (F(3!) + 0!)))$
13431 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - (F(3!) + 1))$
13432 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - F((3 \times 2)))$
13433 := $(1 + (((F(3)^{F(4)})!)/3) - F(3!))$
13434 := $(((((1 + 3) + 4)!)/3) - (F(4)!))$
13436 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) + ((F(3) - (6))))$
13437 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) - F(-((3 - 7))))$
13438 := $((((-1) \times (F(3!)!)/(-F(4))) + ((3! - 8)))$
13439 := $(-1 - (((F(3)^{F(4)})!)/ (3! - 9)))$

13440 := $(1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 0$
13441 := $(1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 1$
13442 := $(1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 2$
13443 := $(1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 3$
13444 := $(1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 4$
13445 := $(1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 5$

$$13446 := (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 6$$

$$13447 := (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 7$$

$$13448 := (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 8$$

$$13449 := (1 + 3 + 4)!/F(4) + 9$$

$$13453 := (-((1 \times 3)) + ((-4) + 5!)^{F(3)})$$

$$13454 := ((1 - 3) + ((-4) + 5!)^{F(F(4))})$$

$$13455 := ((((-1 + 3)!) - F(4)) \times (5! - (5)))$$

$$13456 := ((((-1 + 3)!) - 4)^{F(-5+F(6))})$$

$$13457 := (-1 + (((F(3)!)! / F(4)) + (5 + F(7))))$$

$$13458 := (F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)))) - (F((F(4)!) - ((5! \times F(8))))))$$

$$13460 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 0$$

$$13461 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 1$$

$$13462 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 2$$

$$13463 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 3$$

$$13464 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 4$$

$$13465 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 5$$

$$13466 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 6$$

$$13467 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 7$$

$$13468 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 8$$

$$13469 := -1 + (F(3)!)! / F(4) + F(F(6)) + 9$$

$$13472 := (F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)))) + (((F(4)!) - (7! / (-2))))))$$

$$13473 := (1 + (F(3!) \times (4 - (7! / (-3))))))$$

$$13474 := ((((-1) \times (F(3)!)!) / (-F(4))) + F((F(7) - (4))))$$

$$13475 := ((((-1) \times (F(3)!)!) / (-F(4))) + (7 \times 5))$$

$$13476 := (((1 - F(-(F(3) - 4!))) / (-7)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$13481 := (-1 + (F(3) \times (-4!) + F((F(8) - 1))))$$

$$13482 := (F((1 \times 3)) \times (-4!) + F((F(8) - F(2))))$$

$$13483 := (1 + ((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(4))) + (8! / 3)))$$

$$13484 := ((-1 + F(F(3!))) + ((4! + (8! / F(4))))$$

$$13485 := (F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - ((F((F(4)!)!) / (-((8 - 5)!))))$$

$$13486 := ((1 + F(F(3!))) \times (F(4) + F((F(8) - (6))))$$

$$13488 := ((1 - ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)} - F(F(8)))) \times 8)$$

$$13489 := (((-1) \times F((F(3) + 4!))) - 8)/(-9))$$

$$13493 := ((F(13) \times (4! + F(9))) - F(F(3!)))$$

$$13494 := (((-1 + F((F(3) + 4!)))/9) + (F(4)!))$$

$$13496 := (((-1 + F((F(3) + 4!)))/9) + F(6))$$

$$13499 := ((-1 - F(F(F(3!)))) - (((F(4)! \times (-F(9))) + F(9)))$$

$$13514 := ((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - F((5 + 1))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$13517 := ((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) \times F(F((5 - 1)))) - F(7))$$

$$13520 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 0$$

$$13521 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 1$$

$$13522 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 2$$

$$13523 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 3$$

$$13524 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 4$$

$$13525 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 5$$

$$13526 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 6$$

$$13527 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 7$$

$$13528 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 8$$

$$13529 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 2 + 9$$

$$13540 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 0$$

$$13541 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 1$$

$$13542 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 2$$

$$13543 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 3$$

$$13544 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 4$$

$$13545 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 5$$

$$13546 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 6$$

$$13547 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 7$$

$$13548 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 8$$

$$13549 := (F(-1 + F(F(3!))) + 5) \times F(F(4)) + 9$$

$$13551 := (-1 - ((F(3!) - 5!) \times (5! + 1)))$$

$$13552 := (((-1) \times F(3!)) + 5!) \times (5! + F(2))$$

$$13553 := (1 + ((F(F(3)) + 5!) \times (5! - F(3!))))$$

$$13554 := (((F(13) - 5!) \times 5!) - (F(4)!))$$

$$13555 := (((F(13) - 5!) \times 5!) - (5))$$

$$13560 := (((-1 + 3!))! \times ((5! - F(6)) + 0!))$$

- 13562** := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + (-5 + F(F(6)))) \times 2)$
13563 := $((((1 \times 3) + 5!) + ((F(6)!/3))$
13564 := $((((1 + 3) + 5!) + ((F(6)!/F(4)))$
13565 := $(-1 + ((F(F(3)) - 5!) \times (6 - 5!)))$
13573 := $(((((1 + F(F(3!))) \times 5!) - F(7)) + F(F(F(3!))))$
13582 := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + (5 + F(8))) \times 2)$
13584 := $(((((1 + 3)!) + 5!) + (8!/F(4)))$
13585 := $(-1 + ((F(F(3!)) \times 5!) + ((F(F(8)) + 5!))))$
13586 := $((((-1 + 3!)!) + (5! \times F(8))) + F(F(F(6))))$
13599 := $(-1 + (((3!)! \times 5)/(-9)) \times (-F(9)))$
13615 := $(F((1 + F(F(3!)))) - (F(6)^{-1+5}))$
13623 := $((-((1 \times 3)) + 6!) \times (-2 + F(F(3!))))$
13624 := $(F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + ((F(F(6)) - 2)^{F(4)}))$
13633 := $((-1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(6)!/(-3!) + F(F(3!))))$
13634 := $(F((1 + F(3!))) \times (F((F(6) + 3!) + (4!)))$
13635 := $((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(6)!/(3 \times 5)))$
13636 := $((F((1 + F(3!))) \times (6! + 3)) - F(F(F(6))))$
13639 := $(F(13) - (((F(6)!/(-3)) + F(9)))$
13642 := $((13 + 6) \times (((F(4)!)! - 2))$
13643 := $(1 + ((F(3) - F(F(6))) \times (F(F(4)) - 3!)))$
13644 := $((F((1 + F(3!))) \times 6) + ((F((F(4)!)!)/F(4)))$
13646 := $-((F((1 + F(3!))) + ((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \times (-6!)))$
13648 := $(((-1 + 3!) + F(-((F(6) - 4!))) \times 8)$
13649 := $(F((1 + F(F(3!)))) - ((F(6)^4) - F(9)))$
13654 := $((((F((1 + F(3!))) \times 6!) + 5!) - F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))$
13656 := $(((((1 \times 3)!)! + F((F(F(6)) - (5)))) \times F(6))$
13660 := $(-1 + ((-F(3)) + F(F(6))) \times (6! - 0!))$
13662 := $(1 + ((-F(3)) + F(F(6))) \times (6! - F(2)))$
13664 := $((((1 + 3!) + F((F(6) + F(6)))) \times F((F(4)!)!))$
13667 := $((((13 + 6) \times 6!) - F(7))$
13673 := $(F(13) + ((F(6) \times 7!)/3))$
13674 := $((((-1) \times (3!)!) \times (-6 - F(7))) - (F(4)!))$
13675 := $((((-1) \times (3!)!) \times (-6 - F(7))) - (5))$
13676 := $(-((1 + 3)) - ((-6 - F(7)) \times 6!))$
13678 := $(((-1 - 3!) \times (-6 - F(7))) - (F(8)))$

- 13679 := $(-1 + ((3!)! \times (-(F(6) + (7) - F(9)))))$
 13680 := $((-1) \times (3!)! + ((6! \times (F(8) - 0!)))$
 13681 := $((1 - 3!!) + ((6! \times (F(8) - 1)))$
 13682 := $(F((1 \times 3)) + (6! \times (F(8) - 2)))$
 13684 := $(1 - ((-(3^6) - 8!)/F(4)))$
 13686 := $((F((1 + F(3!))) - (6!)) \times (-F(8)) - (6!))$
 13692 := $((-1) \times F(F(3!))) \times (-(6! + (F(9) \times (-2))))$
 13693 := $(1 + (F(F(3!)) \times (6! - (F(9) \times F(3))))$
 13699 := $((-1 - 3!!) \times ((6 + 9) - F(9)))$
 13728 := $((F(((1 \times 3)!)) \times (F(7)!)) / ((2 + 8)!))$
 13729 := $(1 + ((F(3!) \times (F(7)!)) / ((F(2) + 9)!))$
 13734 := $((-1) \times F(F(3!))) \times ((-7!)/F(3!) - (4!))$
 13736 := $(-1 + ((3! + F(7)) \times (3 + 6!)))$
 13737 := $((1 + (F(3!) \times 7)) \times (F(3!) + F(F(7))))$
 13742 := $(F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!))) + (F(F(7)) \times (4!/2)))$
 13743 := $((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F(7)) \times (4 \times 3)))$
 13744 := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - 7) \times F((F(4)!)) - (F((F(4)!))!))$
 13748 := $((1 - (-F(3)) \times F(F(7))) \times (F(4)! + F(F(8)))$
 13754 := $(-1 + (F(F(3!)) \times ((F(7) \times (-5)) + ((F(4)!)!))$
 13756 := $(1 + (((3!)! - (F(7) \times 5)) \times F(F(6))))$
 13763 := $((((1 + F(3!)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((3!)!))$
 13764 := $((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F(7)) + F((-6) + 4!)))$
 13765 := $((-1 + 3!) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times 5!))$
 13767 := $((-1 + 3!!) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) \times (-7))))$
 13775 := $((-1 + ((F(F(3!)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7)))) \times 5)$
 13777 := $(1 + (F(3!) \times ((-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times (-7)))$
 13783 := $((F(((1 + 3)!)) - (7! - F(8))) / 3)$
 13787 := $((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) - (7!)) \times 8) - F(7)$
 13794 := $((((1 + 3!)! - ((F(7) \times F(9)))) \times F(4))$
 13796 := $(-1 + (((3!)! - (7 \times 9)) \times F(F(6))))$
 13798 := $(1 + (((3!)! - (7 \times 9)) \times F(8)))$
 13822 := $((((1 + 3))!)^{F(8/2)} - 2)$
 13824 := $((((1 + 3))!)^{F(8 \times 2/4)})$
 13826 := $((1 + 3) \times ((8 - 2)! + F(F(F(6))))$

- 13827 := ((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (8!/(2 × 7)))
13832 := (((((1 × 3)!)! + 8) × (F(F(3!) - 2)))
13833 := ((1 + F(3!)) + (((8 × 3)³)))
13834 := ((F(((1 × 3)!) + F(F(8))) - ((3!)! × (-4)))
13843 := (((1 - 3) + F(8)) + (4!³))
13844 := ((-((1³)) + F(8)) + (4!^{F(4)}))
13859 := (-1 + (((3!)!/8) × (5! + F(9))))
13860 := (((((1 + 3)!)!/8) × (F(F(6) + 0!)))
13864 := (((F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + 8) × F(6)) - (F((F(4)!)!))!)
13869 := ((-1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (86 × F(9)))
13896 := (((-1 + 3!)! + (F((8 + 9)))) × 6)
13923 := (((1 + 3!)! + (9 × F((2 × F(3!))))))
13943 := (-1 + ((F(F(3!)) × F((9 × F(F(4)))))) - (F(3!)!))
13944 := ((-(((1 + 3) - 9)!)! + (4!^{F(4)}))
13948 := (-1 + ((3 + F(9)) × F(((F(4)!) + 8))))
13949 := (F(((1 + 3!) + 9)) × (F(4) + F(9)))
13955 := ((F(13) - (9!/5!)) × (-5))
13956 := (-(((1 + 3)!)! - 9!)/(5 + F(F(6))))
13957 := (F(F(F(((1 × 3)!)!))) + ((9!/5!) - F(7)))
13958 := (1 - ((F(3) + 9!)/(-5 - F(8))))
13964 := ((F((1 + F(3!))) × (-F(9))) + (F(F(6)) × ((F(4)!)!))
13965 := ((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((9! - 6!)/5!))
13966 := (1 + (((3!)! - F(9)) - F(F(6))) × F(F(6)))
13972 := (F(F(F(((1 × 3)!)!))) + (F(9) × F((F(7) - 2))))
13973 := (F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + (F(9) × (F(F(7)) - F(F(3!))))))
13974 := ((-1 + ((F(F(3)) + 9) × F(F(7)))) × (F(4)!)
13977 := ((-1 - (F(3)!)! - (-9 - (F(F(7)) × F(F(7))))))
13978 := (((1 + 3)!)! + F(9)) × (F(F(7)) + 8)
13986 := ((((-1 + 3!)! - 9) × (F(8) × 6))
14053 := ((-1 + 4!) × (0! + F((5 × 3))))
14057 := (((1 × 4)!)!^{F(-0!+5)}) + F(F(7))
14147 := (((1 - F(F((F(4)!)!))) × (1 - ((F(4)!)!)) - F(F(7)))
14152 := ((-1 - F((F(4)!)!)) + (((-1 + 5!)²)))
14153 := ((-1) × F((F(4)!)!)) + (((-1 + 5!)^{F(3)})))

- 14154** := $((-1 - (F(4))!) + ((-1 + 5!)^{F(F(4))}))$
14157 := $((1 + F((F(4))!)) \times ((1 + 5!) \times F(7)))$
14162 := $1 + (F(F(F(4))) - (-1 + 6)!)^2$
14167 := $((((1 + 4))! \times -((1 - 6))!) - F(F(7)))$
14187 := $(((-1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (1 - F(8))) - F(F(7)))$
14237 := $((F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 2) + ((3!)! - F(7)))$
14238 := $((-(1 \times 42) + 3!) \times F(8))$
14244 := $((F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 2) + (((F(4))!)! - (F(4))!))$
14245 := $((F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 2) + (((F(4))!)! - (5)))$
14246 := $((F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 2) + (-4 + 6!))$
14250 := $((F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 2) + (((5 + 0))!))$
14253 := $((-1 + (((F(4))! + F(2))! \times 5)) - F(F(F(3))))$
14254 := $((1 + 4) \times ((2 + 5))! - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
14255 := $((-1 - 4!) - ((F(2) - 5!) \times 5!))$
14256 := $(F((14 - 2)) \times (5! - F(F(6))))$
14257 := $((1 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (2 - (-5 \times 7!)))$
14267 := $((1 + (F(4!) \times (2 - 6)))/(-F(7)))$
14283 := $(((-1 + 4!)^2) \times (F(8) + 3!))$
14307 := $((1 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + ((F(3))!)/(- (0! - F(7))))$
14311 := $((((1 + 4))!^{F(3)}) - F(11))$
14313 := $((F((-1 + 4!)) - 31)/F(3))$
14322 := $((F((-1 + 4!)) - F((3! + F(2))))/2)$
14323 := $((F((-1 + 4!)) + F(F(3)))/2 - 3!)$
14324 := $((F((-1 + 4!)) - (3^2))/F(F(4)))$
14325 := $((F((-1 + 4!)) + 3)/2 - (5))$
14328 := $((1 - F(-((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(3!)))))))/(-2) + F(F(8)))$
- 14330** := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 0$
14331 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 1$
14332 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 2$
14333 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 3$
14334 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 4$
14335 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 5$
14336 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 6$
14337 := $(F(-1 + 4!) + 3)/F(3) + 7$

$$14338 := (F(-1 + 4!) + 3) / F(3) + 8$$

$$14339 := (F(-1 + 4!) + 3) / F(3) + 9$$

$$14340 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 0$$

$$14341 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 1$$

$$14342 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 2$$

$$14343 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 3$$

$$14344 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 4$$

$$14345 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 5$$

$$14346 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 6$$

$$14347 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 7$$

$$14348 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 8$$

$$14349 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (3!! - F(4)) + 9$$

$$14350 := (((1 + 4)!)^{F(3)} - (50))$$

$$14352 := (((-1) \times 4!) \times F(3)) + (5!^2)$$

$$14353 := ((1 - (4! \times F(3))) + (5!^{F(3)}))$$

$$14354 := (((1 - 4!) \times F(3)) + (5!^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$14355 := (((-1) \times 4!) - F(F(3!))) + (5! \times 5!)$$

$$14360 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 0$$

$$14361 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 1$$

$$14362 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 2$$

$$14363 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 3$$

$$14364 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 4$$

$$14365 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 5$$

$$14366 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 6$$

$$14367 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 7$$

$$14368 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 8$$

$$14369 := (-1 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-F(3) + 6!) + 9$$

$$14372 := (-1 + (F((-4) + F(F(3!)))) \times (7 + 2)))$$

$$14374 := (1 + ((F(4)^{F(3)}) \times F((-7) + 4!)))$$

$$14375 := ((-1 - 4!) - (((F(3) - (7))))!) \times (-5!))$$

$$14377 := ((1 - 4!) - ((3!) \times (-7) - F(7)))$$

$$14378 := ((-1 - ((F(4)!)!) - (((-3) \times 7!) + F(8)))$$

$$14379 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} + F(7)) - F(9))$$

$$14380 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 0$$

$$14381 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 1$$

$$14382 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 2$$

$$14383 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 3$$

$$14384 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 4$$

$$14385 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 5$$

$$14386 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 6$$

$$14387 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 7$$

$$14388 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 8$$

$$14389 := (1 - F(4)!) \times (F(F(3)) - F(8)) + 9$$

$$14390 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - 9) - 0!)$$

$$14391 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - (9 \times 1))$$

$$14392 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - 9) + F(2))$$

$$14393 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - 9) + F(3))$$

$$14394 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - 9) + F(4))$$

$$14397 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - F((-9) + F(7))))$$

$$14398 := ((-1) \times F((F(4))!) - (((3)! - F(9)) \times (-F(8))))$$

$$14399 := (((((1 + 4))!)^{F(3)} - (9/9))$$

$$14400 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 00$$

$$14401 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 01$$

$$14402 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 02$$

$$14403 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 03$$

$$14404 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 04$$

$$14405 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 05$$

$$14406 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 06$$

$$14407 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 07$$

$$14408 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 08$$

$$14409 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 09$$

$$14410 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 10$$

$$14411 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 11$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14412 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 12 \\ 14413 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 13 \\ 14414 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 14 \\ 14415 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 15 \\ 14416 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 16 \\ 14417 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 17 \\ 14418 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 18 \\ 14419 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 19 \\ 14420 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 20 \\ 14421 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 21 \\ 14422 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 22 \\ 14423 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 23 \\ 14424 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 24 \\ 14425 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 25 \\ 14426 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 26 \\ 14427 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 27 \\ 14428 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 28 \\ 14429 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 29 \\ 14430 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 30 \\ 14431 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 31 \\ 14432 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 32 \\ 14433 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 33 \\ 14434 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 34 \\ 14435 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 35 \\ 14436 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 36 \\ 14437 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 37 \\ 14438 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 38 \\ 14439 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 39 \\ 14440 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 40 \\ 14441 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 41 \\ 14442 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 42 \\ 14443 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 43 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14444 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 44 \\ 14445 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 45 \\ 14446 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 46 \\ 14447 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 47 \\ 14448 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 48 \\ 14449 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 49 \\ 14450 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 50 \\ 14451 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 51 \\ 14452 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 52 \\ 14453 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 53 \\ 14454 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 54 \\ 14455 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 55 \\ 14456 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 56 \\ 14457 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 57 \\ 14458 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 58 \\ 14459 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 59 \\ 14460 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 60 \\ 14461 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 61 \\ 14462 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 62 \\ 14463 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 63 \\ 14464 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 64 \\ 14465 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 65 \\ 14466 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 66 \\ 14467 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 67 \\ 14468 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 68 \\ 14469 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 69 \\ 14470 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 70 \\ 14471 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 71 \\ 14472 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 72 \\ 14473 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 73 \\ 14474 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 74 \\ 14475 &:= (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 75 \end{aligned}$$

$$14476 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 76$$

$$14477 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 77$$

$$14478 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 78$$

$$14479 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 79$$

$$14480 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 80$$

$$14481 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 81$$

$$14482 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 82$$

$$14483 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 83$$

$$14484 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 84$$

$$14485 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 85$$

$$14486 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 86$$

$$14487 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 87$$

$$14488 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 88$$

$$14489 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 89$$

$$14490 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 90$$

$$14491 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 91$$

$$14492 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 92$$

$$14493 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 93$$

$$14494 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 94$$

$$14495 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 95$$

$$14496 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 96$$

$$14497 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 97$$

$$14498 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 98$$

$$14499 := (1 + 4)!^{F(F(4))} + 99$$

$$14507 := (((1 + 4))! \times (5! + 0!)) - F(7)$$

$$14514 := (((1 + 4))! \times (5! + 1)) - (F(4))!$$

$$14520 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 0$$

$$14521 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 1$$

$$14522 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 2$$

$$14523 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 3$$

$$14524 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 4$$

$$14525 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 5$$

$$14526 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 6$$

$$14527 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 7$$

$$14528 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 8$$

$$14529 := (1 + 4)! \times (5! + F(2)) + 9$$

$$14533 := (((1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)) - F(3!)) + F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$14535 := (((1 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 5) - (((F(3))! - 5!))$$

$$14536 := (F(F(F((F(1 \times 4))!))) - (5 \times (F(3) - 6!)))$$

$$14538 := ((-1) \times F((F(4))!)) - ((-5) \times (3!) - F(F(8)))$$

$$14540 := ((-1 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (-5) \times (((F(4))! - 0!)))$$

$$14541 := (((1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)) + F(F(F(((4 - 1))!))))$$

$$14542 := ((1 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (5 \times (((F(4))! - F(2))))$$

$$14543 := (-1 + (((F(4))! \times 5!) + ((4!^3))))$$

$$14544 := (((1^4 + 5))! + (4!^{F(4)}))$$

$$14545 := ((1 + 4!) + ((5!^{F(4)} + 5!))$$

$$14546 := (((((1 + 4))! \times 5!) / 4) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$14547 := (1 + (((F(4))! \times 5) + F((F(4) \times 7))))$$

$$14548 := (((-1) \times ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)) + (F(F(4)) + F(F(8)))$$

$$14551 := (((-1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))$$

$$14554 := (F((1 + F((F(4))!))) + (5! + (5!^{F(4)})))$$

$$14556 := ((((-1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)) + (5)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$14564 := ((F((1 + 4!)) / 5) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)}))$$

$$14565 := (F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) - (5! \times (-65)))$$

$$14566 := (-1 + (((((F(4))! \times 5) + (F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))))$$

$$14568 := (((1 + 4))! \times 5!) + (F(6) \times F(8))$$

$$14573 := (-1 + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-5) + (F(F(7)) \times 3)))$$

$$14574 := ((-1) \times F(F((F(4))!))) \times (5 - (F(F(7)) \times F(4)))$$

$$14586 := (F(F(F((F(1 \times 4))!))) + (-5) \times (-8 - 6!))$$

$$14589 := (((1 + 4))! \times 5!) - (F(8) \times (-9))$$

$$14596 := (((1 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-F((F(-(5 - 9)))))) / (-6))$$

$$14615 := (-1 - ((4! - 6!) \times F(F((1 + 5))))$$

$$14616 := (((-1) \times 4!) + 6!) \times F(F((1 \times 6)))$$

$$14617 := (1 - ((4! - 6!) \times F((1 + 7)))$$

$$14629 := (((-1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-F(F(6)))) - (2^9))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14633 &:= (((1 + (-((F(4) - F(6))))!)^{F(3)}) - F(3!)) \\
 14634 &:= ((-1 - (F(4))!) + ((F(6) + 3)^4)) \\
 14635 &:= ((-1 + ((F(4!)/F(F(6))) + 3!)) \times 5) \\
 14636 &:= (-1 + (((-((4! - 6!)) + F(F(3))) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 14639 &:= (-1 + (4! \times F((((6 - 3)! + 9)))) \\
 14654 &:= (F((1 + (F(4))!)) + (((6 + 5)^4)) \\
 14655 &:= (-1 + ((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) + (5! \times 5!)) \\
 14656 &:= (((((1 + ((F(4))!)) + (F(F(6)))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 14660 &:= ((F((1 + (F(4))!)) + (6!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)) \\
 14662 &:= ((-1 - 4!) - ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(6))!)/2)) \\
 14663 &:= ((-1) \times 4!) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(6))!)/(-F(3))) \\
 14664 &:= ((1 + F((F(4) + (6 + 6)))) \times 4!) \\
 14665 &:= (((1 + 4)^6) - (F(6) \times 5!)) \\
 14666 &:= ((((-1 + ((F(4))!)) - (F(F(6)))) \times F(F(6))) + F(6)) \\
 14667 &:= (1 + (((((F(4))!)) - (F(F(6)))) \times F(F(6))) - F(7)) \\
 14669 &:= (-1 + (((((F(4))!)) - (F(F(6)))) \times F(F(6))) - 9)) \\
 14673 &:= (((F((1 \times 4)) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) - 3!) \\
 14674 &:= (1 + (((F(4) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(7))) - (F(4))!)) \\
 14675 &:= ((1 + 4!) \times ((6! - F(7)) - 5!)) \\
 14679 &:= ((1 + (F(4))!) \times (F((6 + 7)) \times 9)) \\
 \\
 14680 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 0 \\
 14681 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 1 \\
 14682 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 2 \\
 14683 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 3 \\
 14684 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 4 \\
 14685 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 5 \\
 14686 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 6 \\
 14687 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 7 \\
 14688 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 8 \\
 14689 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! - F(F(6))) \times F(8) + 9 \\
 \\
 14692 &:= (((1 + (F((F(4))!))!) - (F(F(F(6))) - 9))/2) \\
 14693 &:= ((F((-1 + 4!)) + ((6! + 9)))/F(3)) \\
 14694 &:= ((F((1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-6)) + (9!/F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 14695** := $(F((1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) - (F(6) \times F((9 + 5))))$
14696 := $((-1) \times F((4! - (6)))) - (-9!)/F(F(6)))$
14697 := $(-1 - ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-6! - 9)) + F(F(7))))$
14698 := $-((F(F((1 + (F(4))!))) - (((6! - 9) \times F(8))))$
14700 := $((-1) \times F(F((F(4))!))) \times (-700)$
14734 := $-(F(14) - ((7! - 3) \times F(4)))$
14735 := $(-1 + (F(4) \times ((7! - F(3!)) - 5!)))$
14736 := $((F((1 \times 4)))! \times (7! - F((3 \times 6))))$
14737 := $(1 + (F(4) \times (7! - (F(3)^7))))$
14742 := $-(F(14) - ((7! \times F(4)) - F(2)))$
14743 := $-(F(14) + (7! \times (F(4) - 3!)))$
14744 := $((1 - ((F(4))!)) + (7 + (F(4!)/F(4))))$
14747 := $-((((((1 + 4))! - 7!) \times F(4)) + F(7))$
14753 := $(-1 + (F(4) \times ((7! - 5!) - F(3))))$
14754 := $((((1 - F(4)) + 7!) - 5!) \times F(4))$
14755 := $((F((1 \times 4)) \times (7! - 5!)) - (5))$
14759 := $((-1 + ((F(4))!)) - ((F(7) \times 5!) \times (-9)))$
14760 := $(F((1 \times 4)) \times (7! - ((6 - 0!)!))$
14761 := $(1 + (F(4) \times (7! - ((6 - 1))!)))$
14763 := $((((-1) \times 4!) + (7)) + 6!) \times F(F(3!))$
14764 := $(1 + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times ((7 + 6!) - 4!))$
14765 := $((F((1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) + 7)/6) \times 5$
14766 := $((1 - 4!) \times ((F(7) \times 6) - 6!))$
14770 := $(((-1 - F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F(7))) \times 70)$
14776 := $((-1 - (4! \times (-77))) \times F(6))$
14783 := $(-1 + (4! \times (F((7 + 8)) + 3!)))$
14785 := $((1 + (F(4) \times 7!)) - (8!/5!))$
14796 := $((1 + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(7))) \times (9 \times 6))$
14820 := $(((-1) \times ((F(4))!)) - (F(8))) \times (-20)$
14822 := $((F((-1 + 4!)) + (F((8 \times 2))))/2)$
14826 := $((-14) + ((8 - 2)!) \times F(F(6)))$
14833 := $(F((-1 + 4!)) - (((8 \times 3)^3))$
14834 := $((1 + (F((F(4))!))! + F((F(8) - F(3))))/F(4))$
14840 := $((1 - F(F((F(4))!))) \times ((-F(8) - ((F(4))!)) - 0!))$
14843 := $((1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-F(8))) - (F(F(4))^{F(3!)})$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14844 &:= (((1 - F(F((F(4))!))) \times (-F(8)) - ((F(4))!)) + 4!) \\
 14846 &:= (-1 + (((F(4))! - F((F(8)/F(4)))) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 14847 &:= ((F((1 + (F(4))!)) \times (-F(8))) + ((F(4) \times 7!)) \\
 14848 &:= (1 - (((F(4))! - F((F(8)/F(4)))) \times (-F(8)))) \\
 14849 &:= (1 + ((F(F(4))⁸) \times (4! + F(9)))) \\
 14863 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(4))⁸)) + (F(F(6)) \times (3)!)) \\
 14864 &:= (-(((1 + F(4))⁸)) + (F(F(6)) \times ((F(4))!)) \\
 14866 &:= (((1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-F(8))) - F((F(F(6)) - F(6)))) \\
 14867 &:= (1 + (((F(4))! \times F(8)) - ((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))))) \\
 14868 &:= ((-((1 \times 4) + 8) + 6!) \times F(8)) \\
 14869 &:= (((-1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-F(8))) - ((F(6) \times F(9)))) \\
 14874 &:= (((1 - ((F(4))!)) \times (-F(8))) - F(F(7)) + F((F(4))!)) \\
 14878 &:= (-1 + (((F(4))! \times F(8)) - (F(F(7)) + 8))) \\
 14879 &:= (1 + (((F(4))! \times F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) + 9)))) \\
 14886 &:= (-1 + (((F(4))! \times F(8)) - F((F(8) - F(6)))) \\
 14887 &:= (((1 - 4) \times 8!) / (-8) - F(F(7))) \\
 14888 &:= (1 + (((F(4))! \times F(8)) - F((-8) + F(8)))) \\
 14897 &:= (1 + (((F(4))! \times F(8)) - (-9) + F(F(7)))) \\
 14905 &:= ((-1 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (((F(9) - 0!) \times 5!)) \\
 14906 &:= (((1 + 4)! \times (F(9) - 0!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 14912 &:= (F(F((1 + (F(4))!))) \times ((9 - 1)²) \\
 14924 &:= (((1 + F(4!)) - F((F(9)/2))) / F(4)) \\
 14925 &:= (F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) - ((F(9) \times (-2)) \times 5!)) \\
 \\
 14930 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 0 \\
 14931 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 1 \\
 14932 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 2 \\
 14933 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 3 \\
 14934 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 4 \\
 14935 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 5 \\
 14936 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 6 \\
 14937 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 7 \\
 14938 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 8 \\
 14939 &:= -1 + ((F(4))! - 9) \times F(F(3!)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14943 &:= ((-1 - (F(F(4))^9)) + (F(4!)/3)) \\
 14944 &:= (-(((1 + F(4))^9)) + (F(4!)/F(4))) \\
 14946 &:= (((1 + ((F(4))!)!) - 9) \times F(F((F(4))!))) - 6) \\
 14947 &:= (1 - (F(4) \times ((F(9) + 4!) - 7!))) \\
 14952 &:= (((1 + ((F(4))!)!) - 9) \times F(F(((5 - 2))!))) \\
 14953 &:= (1 + (((F(4))!)! - F((F(9 - 5))!)) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 14957 &:= (F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F(F((9 - 5)))^{F(7)})) \\
 14960 &:= ((1 + F(F((F(4))!))) \times (F(9) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!))) \\
 14966 &:= (-(((1 + 4))! + F(9))) - (-6!) \times F(F(6))) \\
 14974 &:= (1 - ((49 - 7!) \times F(4))) \\
 14983 &:= ((-1 - (4 \times F(9))) - (-F(8)) \times (3!)) \\
 14984 &:= ((-((1 \times 4)) \times F(9)) + (F(8) \times ((F(4))!))) \\
 14986 &:= ((-1) \times F((F(4))!)) - (-((F(9) \times F(8))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 14988 &:= ((-1) \times (F(4))!) + (((F(9) \times F(8)) \times F(8))) \\
 14993 &:= (-1 + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (F(9) \times F(F((9 - 3)))))) \\
 14995 &:= (1 + ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(9)) \times F(F((F(9 - 5))!)))) \\
 14996 &:= ((1 - 4!) \times ((F(9) + F(9)) - 6!)) \\
 15005 &:= (F(((1 \times 5)^{0!+0!}))/5) \\
 15036 &:= (F(F((1 + 5))) \times (-((0! + 3) - 6!))) \\
 15043 &:= (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + (0! + (4^3))) \\
 15047 &:= (-1 + (F((5 - 0!) \times (-4! - 7!))) \\
 15057 &:= (-F(-((1 - 5))) \times (F(F((0! + 5)))) - (7!)) \\
 15078 &:= ((F(F(-((1 - 5)))) - (-((0! - 7)))!) \times (-F(8))) \\
 15086 &:= -((F((F((1 + 5)) + 0!)) - (F(8) \times 6!)) \\
 15094 &:= (((1 + 5!) + 0!) \times F(9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 15096 &:= (-((-((1 - 5)))!) + (F(-((0! - 9))) \times 6!)) \\
 15117 &:= (F(((1 \times 5) - 1)) \times (-1 + 7!)) \\
 15119 &:= (-1 - (-(((5 + 1))!) \times F(-((1 - 9)))) \\
 \\
 15120 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 0 \\
 15121 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 1 \\
 15122 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 2 \\
 15123 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 3 \\
 15124 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15125 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 5 \\15126 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 6 \\15127 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 7 \\15128 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 8 \\15129 &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times (1 + 2)!! + 9 \\ \\15133 &:= ((F(F((1 + 5))) \times (1 + 3!!)) - F(3!)) \\15134 &:= (-1 + ((5 + ((1 + 3!)!) \times F(4))) \\15135 &:= (F(-((1 - 5))) \times (((1 + 3!)! + (5))) \\15136 &:= (-((1 \times 5)) + ((1 + 3!!) \times F(F(6)))) \\15137 &:= (-1 + (F((5 - 1)) \times (3! + 7!))) \\15138 &:= -((F(-((1 - 5))) - ((-1 - 3!!) \times (-F(8)))) \\15140 &:= ((F(F((1 + 5))) \times (1 + ((F(4))!)) - 0!) \\15141 &:= (F(F((1 + 5))) \times (1 + (((4 - 1))!)) \\15142 &:= ((F(F((1 + 5))) \times (1 + ((F(4))!)) + F(2)) \\15143 &:= (F(F(-((1 - 5)))) + ((1 + ((F(4))!)) \times F(F(3!)))) \\15144 &:= (((((1 + 5) + 1))! \times F(4)) + 4!) \\15146 &:= ((1 \times 5) - ((-1 - ((F(4))!)) \times F(F(6)))) \\15147 &:= (F(-((1 - 5))) \times ((1 + F((F(4))!)) + (7!))) \\15162 &:= (F(F((1 + 5))) \times (((1 \times 6))! + 2)) \\15163 &:= (1 + (F(F((5 + 1))) \times (6! + F(3)))) \\15174 &:= ((-1 + F((5 + F((1 + 7)))))/F((F(4))!)) \\15183 &:= (((((1 + 5) + 1))! + F(8)) \times 3) \\15204 &:= (F(F((1 + 5))) \times (((2 + 0!)!)! + 4)) \\15224 &:= (-1 + ((5 + ((F((2 + 2))!)) \times F(F((F(4))!)))) \\15226 &:= (1 - ((5 + ((F((2 + 2))!)) \times (-F(F(6)))) \\15234 &:= ((F((F(F((1 + 5))) - 2)) \times (-3!)) + (F((F(4))!))!)) \\15238 &:= (((-1 + 5!) - F(2)) - ((3!)! \times (-F(8))) \\15243 &:= (((1 + 5!) + 2) + (((F(4))!)) \times F(F(3!))) \\15244 &:= ((F(15) \times (F(2) + 4!)) - (F(4))!) \\15245 &:= ((F(15) \times (F(2) + 4!)) - (5)) \\15246 &:= (((1 + 5!) \times F((2 \times 4))) \times 6) \\15248 &:= (((1 + 5!) + F((-2) + F(F((F(4))!)))) + F(F(8))) \\15249 &:= (-1 + ((5^2) \times F((4! - 9))) \\15264 &:= ((F(15) + (26)) \times 4!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15266 &:= (F(F(((1+5)+2))) - (6! \times (-6))) \\15267 &:= (F(((1+5)+2)) \times (6! + (7))) \\15268 &:= (1 - ((-(5+2) - 6!) \times F(8))) \\15288 &:= (((((1+5))! \times F(2)) + 8) \times F(8)) \\15309 &:= (F(F((1+5))) \times ((3!)! + 09)) \\15312 &:= ((F((-((1-5)))!)/3) - (F(12))) \\15330 &:= (F(F((1+5))) \times ((3^3!) + 0!)) \\15333 &:= ((-((1-5)))! - (F(F(3!)) \times (-3^3!))) \\15335 &:= ((F((-((1-5)))!)/3) - (F(F(3)) + 5!)) \\15336 &:= (((1+5)^3) + ((3!)! \times F(F(6)))) \\15343 &:= (((1-5!) + 3!) + (F(4!)/3)) \\15344 &:= ((-1 - (-5!) \times F(3!)) \times (4 \times 4)) \\15347 &:= (((F(F((1+5))) \times (3!)! - (F(4))!) + F(F(7))) \\15351 &:= (((1+5!) + F(3!)) \times (5! - 1)) \\15352 &:= (((-1+5!) \times F(3!)) + (5!^2)) \\15353 &:= (1 + (((-5!) - F(3!)) \times (-5!)) - F(3!)) \\15354 &:= ((((-1) \times 5!) - F(3!)) \times (-5!)) - (F(4))! \\15355 &:= ((((-1) \times 5!) - F(3!)) \times (-5!)) - (5) \\15356 &:= (((1+5!)^{F(3)} - (5)) + 6!) \\15359 &:= (-1 - (5! \times (F(F(3)) - (5! + 9)))) \\ \\15360 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 0 \\15361 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 1 \\15362 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 2 \\15363 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 3 \\15364 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 4 \\15365 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 5 \\15366 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 6 \\15367 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 7 \\15368 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 8 \\15369 &:= (F(1+5))! \times F(3!)/F(F(6)) + 9 \\ \\15372 &:= (F(F((1+5))) \times ((3!)! + (F(7) - F(2)))) \\15373 &:= (1 + (((5+3!) + 7) \times F(F(3)))) \\15374 &:= (((1+5!)^{F(3)} + F(7)) + ((F(4))!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15375 &:= (15 + ((F(3)^7) \times 5!)) \\15376 &:= (((-1) \times F((5 \times 3))) + 7!) + F(F(F(6))) \\15377 &:= (((-(1 - 5))!) - (-3 \times 7!)) + F(F(7)) \\15378 &:= (-((F(15) - F(3)) - 7!)) + F(F(8)) \\15383 &:= ((-1 - 5!) - (-3!) \times F((F(8) - 3))) \\15384 &:= (((F((1 + 5)))! \times F(3!)) / F(8)) + (4!) \\15386 &:= ((-1 + (5!^{F(3)})) + F((8 + F(6)))) \\15387 &:= (F(-(1 - 5)) \times (F((3 + 8)) + 7!)) \\15388 &:= (1 + ((5!^{F(3)} + F((8 + 8)))) \\15392 &:= (((1 \times 5)^{3!}) - F(F((9 - 2)))) \\15393 &:= (F(F((1 + 5))) \times ((3!)! + F((9 - F(3)))) \\15394 &:= ((F(15) \times F(F(3!))) + F((9 \times F(F(4)))) \\15414 &:= (F(F((1 + 5))) \times ((F(4)!)! + 14)) \\15415 &:= (-1 - ((5! - F(4!)) / F(-(1 - 5)))) \\15424 &:= ((1 + (5! \times F(F(4)))) \times (2^{F(4)!})) \\15426 &:= (((F((1 + 5)))! / (F(4)^2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\15428 &:= ((F(-(1 - 5))!) / F(4) - 28) \\15431 &:= -(((-(1 - 5))!) - ((F(4!) / 3) - 1)) \\15432 &:= (((-(1 - 5))! - (F(4!) / 3)) \times (-F(2))) \\15433 &:= ((1 - 5!) - ((F(4)!)^{3!} / (-3))) \\15434 &:= (((-(1 + 5)) - F(4!)) / (-3) - (4!)) \\15436 &:= (((F(-(1 - 5))) + F(4!)) / 3 - F(F(6))) \\15437 &:= (-((1 + 5)) - ((F(4!) / (-3)) + F(7))) \\15438 &:= (1 + (((-5!) + F(4!)) / 3) + (F(8))) \\15439 &:= (((-(1 - 5))! - F(4!)) / (-3) - 9) \\15440 &:= (-15 - ((F(4!) / (-F(4))) + 0!)) \\15441 &:= (-15 - (F(4!) / (-4 - 1))) \\15442 &:= (-15 - ((F(4!) / (-F(4))) - F(2))) \\15443 &:= (((-15) + F(4!)) - (4!)) / 3 \\15444 &:= (((-(1 + 5)) \times (F(4)!) + F(4!)) / F(4)) \\15445 &:= (-((1 + 5)) - ((F(4!) / (-F(4))) + (5))) \\15446 &:= (((1 + 5) - F(4!)) / (-F(4))) - F(6) \\15447 &:= (((1 + 5) - F(4!)) / (-F(4))) - 7 \\15449 &:= (((F(F((1 + 5))) - F(4!)) \times (-F(4))) / 9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15450 &:= (-(1+5) + (F(4!)/F((5-0!)))) \\15451 &:= ((15 - F(4!))/(-F((5-1)))) \\15452 &:= ((1-5) - (F(4!)/(-(5-2)))) \\15453 &:= (((-(1-5)) - F(4!)) + (5))/(-3) \\15454 &:= (((1^5) - F(4!)) + (5))/(-F(4)) \\15455 &:= ((F(-(1-5)!)/F(4) - (5/5)) \\15457 &:= ((F(-(1-5)!)/F(4) + F(-(5-7))) \\15458 &:= ((-(1+5)) - F(4!))/(5-8) \\15459 &:= (F(-(1-5)) + (F(4!)/F(-(5-9)))) \\15461 &:= ((F(-(1-5)!)/F(4) + (6-1)) \\15462 &:= ((1+5) - (F(4!)/(-(6/2)))) \\15463 &:= ((F(F(1+5)) + F(4!))/(6-3) \\15469 &:= ((F(-(1-5)!)/F(4) - ((F(F(6)) - F(9)))) \\15470 &:= ((F(-(1-5)!)/F(4) + (F(7) + 0!)) \\15473 &:= (-1 + (((-5!) + F(F(4))) - (7!)) \times (-3)) \\15474 &:= (((1+5!) - F(4) + 7!) \times F(4) \\15475 &:= (-(1 \times 5) + (F(4) \times (7! + 5!))) \\15477 &:= (((-(1-5)! + ((F(4)^7))) \times 7) \\15478 &:= (((1 \times 5)^{F(4)!}) - (7 \times F(8))) \\15479 &:= (((1+5!) \times (F(F(4))^7)) - 9) \\15483 &:= (((1+5!) \times F(4)) - (-(F(8)) \times (3)!)) \\15484 &:= (F(F(1+5)) - ((F(4!) + (F(8)))/(-F(4)))) \\15485 &:= (1 + ((5^{F(4)!}) - ((F(8) + 5!)))) \\15490 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 0 \\15491 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 1 \\15492 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 2 \\15493 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 3 \\15494 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 4 \\15495 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 5 \\15496 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 6 \\15497 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 7 \\15498 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 8 \\15499 &:= F((-1+5)!)/F(4) + F(9) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15504 &:= ((1 + 5) \times F((5 + 0!) \times F(4))) \\
 15534 &:= ((1 + 5) \times (5 + F((3! \times F(4)))) \\
 15539 &:= ((-1) \times 5!) + ((5^3!) + F(9)) \\
 15574 &:= (((-1 - (5! \times (-5))) \times F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 15603 &:= (-((1 - (5^6))) - F(F((03)!)) \\
 15604 &:= -((F(F((1 + 5))) - ((6 - 0!)^{F(4)!})) \\
 15605 &:= ((1 + (5^6)) - F(F((0! + (5)))) \\
 15606 &:= (((1 + (5^6)) + 0!) - F(F(6))) \\
 15607 &:= (((((1 + 5)!) \times (F(F(6)) + 0!)) - F(F(7))) \\
 15627 &:= ((1 + (5^6)) + (F(2)^7!)) \\
 15659 &:= (((1 \times 5)^{6!/5!}) + F(9)) \\
 15660 &:= ((1 + (5^6)) + F((F(6) + 0!)) \\
 15664 &:= ((F(F(-(1 - 5))))^{F(6)+6}) - ((F(4)!))! \\
 15666 &:= (((((1 \times 5) + F(F(6))) + (6!)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 15687 &:= ((F(F((1 + 5))) \times F((F(6) + 8))) - (7!)) \\
 15724 &:= (F(15) + ((7! - 2) \times F(4))) \\
 \\
 15730 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 0 \\
 15731 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 1 \\
 15732 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 2 \\
 15733 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 3 \\
 15734 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 4 \\
 15735 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 5 \\
 15736 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 6 \\
 15737 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 7 \\
 15738 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 8 \\
 15739 &:= F(15) + 7! \times 3 + 9 \\
 \\
 15743 &:= ((F(15) + F(7)) + (((F(4)!))! \times F(F(3)))) \\
 15744 &:= ((-1 + 5!) + ((7 - F(F(4)))^{F(4)!})) \\
 15746 &:= ((1 + 5!) + ((7 - F(F(4)))^6)) \\
 15747 &:= (F(-(1 - 5)) \times (F(F(7)) - ((4! - 7!))) \\
 15774 &:= (((-(15) + 7!) + F(F(7))) \times F(4)) \\
 15776 &:= ((((-(15)!)/(F(7)!)) + (7!)) + F(F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15816 &:= -(((-(1-5)))! - (((F(8)+1) \times 6!))) \\15818 &:= ((-1 + ((-(5-8))!)) \times (1 + F(8))) \\15824 &:= (((F(15) \times 8) - 2) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\15827 &:= ((1-5!) \times ((F(8)-2) \times (-7))) \\15834 &:= ((1 - F((5!/8))) \times (-F(3) + 4!)) \\15835 &:= (((1^5) + F(8)) \times (3!) - (5)) \\15836 &:= ((1-5) - ((F(8) + F(F(3))) \times (-6!))) \\15837 &:= -(((F(F(-(1-5))) - F(F(8))) - (F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)))))) \\15838 &:= (-1 + ((F((5+8)) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(8)))) \\15839 &:= ((-(1^5) + 8!) + ((3!) \times (-F(9)))) \\ \\15840 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 0 \\15841 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 1 \\15842 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 2 \\15843 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 3 \\15844 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 4 \\15845 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 5 \\15846 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 6 \\15847 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 7 \\15848 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 8 \\15849 &:= (1+5)! \times F(8) + F(4)!! + 9 \\ \\15854 &:= ((F(15) \times (F(8) + (5))) - (F(4))!) \\15857 &:= ((-1 + (5^{(8-5)!})) + F(F(7))) \\15860 &:= (F(15) \times ((F(8) + (6)) - 0!)) \\15861 &:= (((1+5)! + (F(8) \times (6! + 1))) \\15862 &:= (((1^5) + F(8)) \times (6! + F(2))) \\15866 &:= (((-1) \times 5!) + F(F(8))) + ((F(6))! / F(6)) \\15867 &:= (((1-5!) + F(F(8))) + (6! \times 7)) \\15873 &:= (((1-5!) + F(F(8))) + ((7! + 3!))) \\15874 &:= ((((-1) \times 5!) + F(F(8))) + (7!)) + F((F(4))!) \\15876 &:= ((F(15) + F(F(8))) + ((7! - 6!))) \\15887 &:= (((-1) \times 5!) + F(F(8))) + ((F(8) + 7!)) \\15897 &:= (F(F(F((1+5)))) - (89 - 7!)) \\15934 &:= (((F((1+5)))! / 9) \times 3!) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))\end{aligned}$$

- 15936** := (((-(1 - 5))! × F(9)) + ((3!)! × F(F(6))))
15937 := (((-(15) - F(9)) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (7!))
15938 := (-1 + (((5 + F(9)) + 3!!) × F(8)))
15944 := (((1 - 5!) × (-F(9)) - F((F(4))!))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))
15946 := ((1 - 5!) × (F(9) - (F((F(4))!) × F(F(6))))))
15947 := (((-(1 × 5)) - F(9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (7!))
15952 := (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - ((F(9) - ((5 + 2))!)))
15957 := (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - ((F(9) - (5)) - 7!))
15967 := (((15 - F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (7!))
15973 := ((F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - (F(9) - 7!)) + F(F(3!)))
15974 := (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - ((9 - 7!) + F(4)))
15976 := ((-((1⁵) + 9)) + 7!) + F(F(F(6)))
15978 := (((1⁵) - 9) + 7!) + F(F(8))
15983 := (((1 + (F(-(5 - 9))))!)! + (F(F(8)) - 3))
15984 := (((1 × 5))! - 9) × F((8 + 4))
15986 := (F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + (((9 - 8) + 6))!)
15987 := ((1 + F((-5) + F(9) - 8)) + (7!))
15997 := ((F(F(F((1 + 5)))) - 9!) / (-9 - F(7)))
16038 := ((1 + F(F(6))) × ((0! + 3!!) + 8))
16039 := (1 + ((F(F(6)) + 0!) × ((3!)! + 9)))
16047 := (((1 + 60) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (7!))
16073 := ((1 + ((F(F(6)) + 0!) × F(F(7)))) + F(F(F(3!))))
16098 := ((F(((1 - 6) - 0!)!)/9) + F(F(8)))
16114 := (F((1 + F(F(6)))) - F((11 + (F(4))!)))
16134 := (((1 - ((6 + 1))!) × 3!) + F(4!))
16136 := ((1 + ((F(6))! / (-1 + F(F(3!)))))) × F(6)
16147 := ((161 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (7!))
16224 := (((F((1 + 6)) × 2)²) × 4!)
16244 := (((-((-((1 - 6)))!) + F((-2) + F(F((F(4))!)))))) × 4)
16254 := (((-1 + 6!) + F((2 × 5))) × F(F((F(4))!)))
16263 := (F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((2 × 6!) + F(3!)))
16264 := -(((1 - 6))! - (2^{F(6)+F(4)}))
16271 := (F((1 + F(F(6)))) + (-2) × ((7 - 1)!))
16293 := (-F(16)) + ((F(2) × 9!) / F(F(3!)))
16294 := (-((F(16) - F(2))) - (-9!) / F(F((F(4))!)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 16296 &:= (((1 + 6!) + F((F(2) + 9))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 16302 &:= ((1 + F(F(6))) \times (F(F(3!)) + (((0! + 2)!)!)) \\
 16303 &:= (1 + (-((F(F(6)) + 3!)) \times (-0! - F(F(3!)))) \\
 16307 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) + (3! \times (-0! - F(F(7)))) \\
 16313 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((3! \times F(13)))) \\
 16323 &:= ((1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(3!)) \times (-2^{F(3!)}))) \\
 16324 &:= (((1 + F(F(6))) + 3!) \times (-2 + 4!)) \\
 16327 &:= (((1 \times 6)!) \times (F(F(3!)) + 2) - F(F(7))) \\
 16339 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (F(3) \times ((3!)! - F(9)))) \\
 16343 &:= (-1 + 6)^{3!} - F(F(4)) + 3! \\
 16344 &:= (((1 + 6)!) / F(3)) + (4!^{F(4)}) \\
 16345 &:= (-1 + 6)^{3!} + F(4)! \times 5! \\
 16346 &:= ((1 + 6!) + ((F(3) + F(4))^6)) \\
 16353 &:= ((F((1 \times 6)) + 3!) + (5^{3!})) \\
 16354 &:= (F((1 + F(6))) \times (F(F(3)) - (5! \times (-4)))) \\
 16359 &:= (F(F((1 \times 6))) \times ((3!)! + 59)) \\
 16363 &:= ((-1) \times F(F(6))) + (F(3)^{F(6)+3!}) \\
 16364 &:= ((1 - F(F(6))) + (F(3)^{F(6)+F(4)!})) \\
 16365 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(6)))) + (((F(3!)! / F(F(6))) \times 5)) \\
 16366 &:= (-1 + 6)^{3!} + F(F(6)) + 6! \\
 16385 &:= (1 + ((F(6)^{3!}) / (F(8) - (5)))) \\
 16404 &:= ((-1 + F(F(6))) + (4^{0!+F(4)!})) \\
 16406 &:= ((1 + F(F(6))) + (4^{0!+6})) \\
 16414 &:= (-((1 + (6^4))) + F((1 + F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 16415 &:= (F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (((F(4)!)^{-1+5})) \\
 16420 &:= ((((-1) \times F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(4))) / 2) + 0! \\
 16423 &:= (1 + ((6! - (F(4)!) \times 23)) \\
 16432 &:= (1 - (((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(4)!)) \times 3) / (-2))) \\
 16434 &:= ((1 + F(F(6))) \times ((F(4) + 3!) + (4!))) \\
 16436 &:= (((1 + F(6)) \times F((-((F(4)!) + F(F(3!)))))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 16437 &:= (F((-1 + F(F(6)))) - ((-4!) - 3!) \times F(7)) \\
 16439 &:= ((-1 - 6!) + ((F((4 + 3))!) / 9!)) \\
 16440 &:= (-((-((1 - 6)!)!)) + (((F(4)!)! \times (4! - 0!))) \\
 16442 &:= (F(16) - ((F(4)! / (-F(4))) + F(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 16443** := $((F(16) \times F(4)) + F(4!))/3$
16444 := $(F(16) - ((-F(4)) - F(4!))/F(4))$
16445 := $(-((1 - (6 \times 4))) \times (((F(4)!)! - (5)))$
16448 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) + (4!)) \times F((F(4)!) \times 8)$
16449 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (((F(4)!)^4 - F(9)))$
16457 := $((-1 + (-F(F(6))) \times (F((F(4)!) - 5!))) \times 7)$
16463 := $(-1 - (-6) \times (((F(4)!) + F(6))^3))$
16465 := $(-1 + 6)^{F(4)!} + 6! + 5!$
16466 := $((-((1 - 6)))! \times 46) + F(F(F(6)))$
16467 := $(-1 + 6)^{F(4)!} + F(F(F(6)))/F(7)$
16469 := $(-((1 - 6)) + (4! \times (6! - F(9))))$
16473 := $((-F(F((1 + 6)))) + ((F(4)!)! + (7!)) + F(F(F(3!))))$
16474 := $((1 + ((F(6) \times ((F(4)!)!) - F(F(7)))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))$
16493 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((4! + F(9)) \times F(F(3!))))$
16497 := $(((((1 + 6))!/4) + 9) \times F(7))$
16498 := $((((1 + 6))! + ((F(F(4))^9) + F(F(8))))$
16536 := $(((-1 + 6!) \times ((5 - F(F(3))))!) - (6!))$
16538 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) \times ((5 - F(F(3))))!) + F(F(8)))$
16544 := $((-F(F((1 + 6)))) \times (5! + F((F(4)!)!)) + F(4!))$
16547 := $((-1 - F(F(F(6)))) + ((5! - F(F(4))) \times F(F(7))))$
16548 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) \times (5! - F(F(4)))) - F(F(8)))$
16555 := $((F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (5! \times 5!)) \times 5)$
16567 := $(((-1 + F(F(6))) \times (5! + 6!)) - F(F(7)))$
16574 := $((((1 + 6)^5) - F((7 + (F(4)!)!)))$
16583 := $((-1 - 6!) \times ((-5) - F(8)) + 3)$
16586 := $(((((1 + 6))! - 5!) + F(F(8))) + (6!))$
16587 := $((((1 + 6!) - 5!) + F(F(8))) + (7!))$
16614 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((6! + F(14))))$
16632 := $((1 + F(F(6))) \times (6! + (3!^2)))$
16634 := $((((-1 + 6!) - F(6)) \times F(3!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))$
16643 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((6! - F((F(4)!)!)) \times F(3!)))$
16653 := $(-F(16)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5! + 3!))$
16659 := $(-1 - ((F(F(F(6)) - 6) - 5!) \times (-F(9))))$
16664 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) + (6!)) \times 6) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))$

- 16665** := $((F(16) + (6! \times (-6))) \times (-5))$
16666 := $(((((1 + 6!) - (6)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))$
16674 := $(F(F((1 \times 6))) \times (6! + 74))$
16684 := $((((-1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)))) - (-8) \times ((F(4))!))$
16686 := $((((1 + (F(6) \times 6!)) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6)))$
16689 := $((((-1 + 6!) \times F(6)) + F(F(8))) - 9)$
16694 := $(-1 - (F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) - ((F(9) \times 4!))))$
16696 := $(((-1 + 6!) \times F(F(6))) + F((9 + F(6))))$
16697 := $(F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + (((6! - 9) + 7!))$
16698 := $((1 + ((F(6) \times 6!) - 9)) + F(F(8)))$
16703 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) + ((7! / (0! - 3!)))$
16704 := $((((1 + (F(6))!) + (7!)) - F(-(0! - 4!)))$
16705 := $((-1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (-7! - ((0! + (5))))!)$
16706 := $((-1 + F(F(F(6)))) + (((7! + 0!) + 6!))$
16707 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) + (((7 - 0!)! + (7!))$
16708 := $(((((1 + 6!) + 7!) + 0!) + F(F(8)))$
16714 := $(((-1 - 6!) \times (-7 + 1)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))$
16731 := $(-((F(16) - (7))) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1)))$
16732 := $(-(((1 - 6))! + (7!)) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2)))$
16734 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(7)) + 3!!) + (4!))$
16739 := $((-1 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((7! + 3!!) + F(9)))$
16743 := $((1 + F((F(6) + F(7)))) + (F(4!) / F(3!)))$
16748 := $((-1 + F(F(F(6)))) + (7 + (F(4!) / 8)))$
16753 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(7)) + (5)) + 3!!))$
16758 := $((1 \times 6) \times ((F(7) + 5!) \times F(8)))$
16763 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) - ((-7 - 6!) \times F(3!))$
16766 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) - (F(6) - 6!))$
16773 := $(((((1 + F(6))! / 7!) \times F(F(7))) - 3)$
16774 := $(((((1 + F(6))! / 7!) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(4)))$
16776 := $(((((1 + F(6))! / 7!) \times F((7 + 6)))$
16777 := $(((((1 + F(6))! \times F(F(7))) + (7!)) / 7!)$
16784 := $(((((1 + F(6)) \times F(F(7))) \times 8) + F((F(4))!))$
16793 := $(((-1 + (-F(6) \times F(F(7)))) \times (-9)) + F(3!))$
16797 := $(F(F((1 \times 6))) + (F(F(7)) \times (9! / 7!))$
16824 := $(((((1 \times 6))! - F(8)) + 2) \times 4!)$

- 16837** := $(1 + (((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times F(3)) - (7!))$
16840 := $(((-1 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(8)))/F((F(4)! + 0!))$
16843 := $(F((-1 + F(F(6)))) + ((8!/4) - F(3)))$
16844 := $(-(((1 + 6)!)) + ((F(F(8)) - 4) \times F(F(4))))$
16845 := $(F((-1 + F(F(6)))) + (84 \times 5!))$
16846 := $(-(((1 + 6)!)) + ((F(F(8)) \times F(F(4))) - 6))$
16848 := $(((-(((1 + 6)!)) + F(F(8))) - 4) + F(F(8)))$
16852 := $(-(((1 + 6)!)) + (F(F(8)) \times F((5 - 2))))$
16853 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(8)) - ((5 + F(3))))!))$
16854 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(8) \times 5!)) \times F(F(4)))$
16857 := $(F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + (F(F(8)) - (-5 + 7!))$
16864 := $(-(((1 + 6)!)) + ((F(F(8)) + 6) \times F(F(4))))$
16866 := $((((-1 + 6!) + F(8)) \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))$
16873 := $((F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + ((F(F(8)) - (7!))) + F(F(3!)))$
16874 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(8)) - (7!))) + F(F((F(4)!)))$
16923 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(9) \times 2) + 3!))$
16927 := $((F((1 + 6)))!/9! - F((F(2) \times F(7))))$
16934 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(9) + 3) \times F(F((F(4)!))))$
16936 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(9) + 3!) + F(F(6))))$
16963 := $(F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(9) + 6!) - 3!))$
16973 := $(((((1 + 6)! + F((9 + 7))) + F(F(F(3!))))$
16977 := $(((-1 - 6!) + F((9 + F(7)))) - F(7))$
16981 := $(((-1 - 6!) - 9) + F((F(8) + 1)))$
16982 := $(((-1) \times 6!) - 9) + F((F(8) + F(2)))$
16983 := $((F((F((1 + 6)) + 9)) - 8) - 3!)$
16984 := $((((-1 - (F(6)!)) - 9) + F(F(8))) + F(4!))$
16986 := $((1 + 6!) + F(9)) \times 8 + F(F(F(6)))$
16992 := $((1 - 6!) + F((9 + F((9 - 2))))$
16994 := $(F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) - ((9!/9) - F(4!)))$
16995 := $((1 + F(F(F(6)))) + (((9! + 9!)/5!))$
16996 := $((F((1 \times 6)))! + ((F(9) \times (F(9) - 6!)))$
17046 := $((-1 - F(F(7))) - ((0 - 4!) \times 6!))$
17047 := $((F((-1 + F(7))) \times ((0! + (4)!)) - F(F(7)))$
17048 := $((1 - F(F(7))) + (((0! + F((F(4)!)))!/F(8)))$
17053 := $(F(17) - (F((-((0! - 5))))!)/(-3))$

$$17134 := (((1 + F(F(7))) \times ((-1 + 3!))!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$17135 := (-1 - (F((F(7) - 1)) \times (F(F(3)) - 5!)))$$

$$17136 := (F((-1 + F(7))) \times (-1 + ((-3) + F(6))!))$$

$$17138 := (-1 + (((F(7))! / ((1 + F(3))!)) - (F(8))))$$

$$17139 := -((F((1 + 7)) - ((13)! / 9!))$$

$$17147 := (((F((1 \times 7)))! / ((1 + F((F(4))!)))! - F(7))$$

$$17154 := (((-1 + F((F(7) - 1))) \times 5!) - (F(4))!)$$

$$17155 := (((-1 + F((F(7) - 1))) \times 5!) - (5))$$

$$17160 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 0$$

$$17161 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 1$$

$$17162 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 2$$

$$17163 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 3$$

$$17164 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 4$$

$$17165 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 5$$

$$17166 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 6$$

$$17167 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 7$$

$$17168 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 8$$

$$17169 := 1 \times F(7)! / (1 + F(6))! + 9$$

$$17184 := (((F((1 \times 7)))! / ((1 + 8))!) + (4!))$$

$$17223 := (((-1 + F(F(7))) + F(22)) - 3!))$$

$$17224 := ((F(F((1 \times 7))) + F(22)) - ((F(4))!))$$

$$17232 := (((-(1 - 7))! - 2) \times ((F(3) + 2))!)$$

$$17243 := (((-1 - F(F(7))) \times 2) + F((4! - F(3))))$$

$$17244 := ((-1 + (F(F(7)) \times (-2))) + F((4! - F(F(4)))))$$

$$17248 := (((-1 + ((7 - F(2))!)) \times 4!) - 8)$$

$$17253 := ((-1 - ((F(F(7)) + 2) \times (-5!)) - F(F(F(3!))))$$

$$17254 := (((F(F((1 \times 7))) + 2) \times 5!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$17258 := (-1 - ((F((F(7) - F(2))) \times (-5!)) + (F(8))))$$

$$17264 := ((1 + 7) - ((F(2) - 6!) \times 4!))$$

$$17266 := ((-1 - F(7)) + (((2 - 6))! \times 6!))$$

$$17267 := (((((1 + 7) / 2)! \times 6!) - F(7))$$

$$17268 := ((1 - F(7)) + (((F(2) + F(6))! / F(8)))$$

$$17273 := (-((1 \times 7)) + (((2 + 7)! / F(F(3!))))$$

$$17274 := (((-(1-7))! + (-2+7!)) \times F(4))$$

$$17279 := (-1 - (((7+2)!/(F(7) - F(9))))$$

$$17280 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 0$$

$$17281 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 1$$

$$17282 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 2$$

$$17283 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 3$$

$$17284 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 4$$

$$17285 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 5$$

$$17286 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 6$$

$$17287 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 7$$

$$17288 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 8$$

$$17289 := (1 \times 7 + 2)!/F(8) + 9$$

$$17293 := (F((1 \times 7)) + ((F(2) \times 9!)/F(F(3!))))$$

$$17294 := ((1 + F(7)) + ((F(2) \times 9!)/F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$17296 := (((1 + 7) \times 2) - (-9!)/F(F(6)))$$

$$17298 := (((1 + F((7 \times 2))) + 9!)/F(8))$$

$$17313 := ((-F((1 + F(7)))) - F(F(3!))) + F((1 + F(F(3!))))$$

$$17326 := (-((F((1 + F(7))) + F(3!))) + F((F(2) + F(F(6))))$$

$$17327 := ((-F((1 + F(7)))) + F((F(F(3!)) + F(2)))) - 7$$

$$17328 := -(((F((1 + F(7))) + 3!) - F((F(2) + F(8))))$$

$$17331 := (-((F((1 + F(7))) + 3)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1)))$$

$$17332 := (-((F((1 + F(7))) + F(3))) + F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))))$$

$$17333 := ((-1 - F((7 \times F(3)))) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(3!))))$$

$$17334 := (-((1 - 7)) + ((F(3) + 3!) \times 4!))$$

$$17336 := (((1 \times 7) + (3 \times (3!)!)) \times F(6))$$

$$17340 := (-((F((1 + F(7))) - 3!)) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!)))$$

$$17342 := (F((1 + F(7))) \times ((F(3) \times 4!) - 2))$$

$$17343 := ((-1) \times F(F(7))) + (((F(3) + 4!)^3))$$

$$17344 := ((1 - F(F(7))) + (((F(3) + 4!)^{F(4)}))$$

$$17345 := (-1 + ((-7) \times F(F(3!))) \times (F(F(4)) - 5!))$$

$$17347 := ((-F((1 + F(7)))) + F(-((F(3) - 4!))) + F(7))$$

$$17352 := (((-(1-7))! + 3) \times ((5 - F(2))!))$$

$$17353 := (((-1 + F(7))^3) + (5^{3!}))$$

- 17358 := (((1 - F(F(7))) × (-F(3) + 5!)) - F(F(8)))
17359 := ((-1 - 7!) + (((F(3)!) × (-5))/(-9)))
17363 := (-((F((-1 + F(7))) - (3^{F(6)}))) + F(F(F(3))))
17364 := ((-1 + F(7)) + ((3 + 6!) × 4!))
17376 := (((1 - F(F(7))) × (-3! × F(7))) - (6!))
17378 := (((1 - F(F(7))) × (-3!)) + (7!)) + F(F(8)))
17396 := (((1 - F(F(7)))/(-F(3))) - (-9!)/F(F(6)))
17408 := (((1 + 7)^{F(4)}) × F((0! + 8)))
17423 := ((-1 - 7!) - ((F(4!)/(-2)) + 3!))
17425 := (1 - (F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))))) × (-F(2) + 5!))
17426 := (F(F((1 + 7))) + ((F(4)²) × 6!))
17433 := ((-1) × F(F(7))) + (((F((F(4)!)!)/3!) + F(F(F(3))))
17434 := (((1 - F(F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) + ((F(3)!)!/(F(4)!)!))
17436 := ((-1 + F(7)) + (4! × (3! + 6!)))
17437 := (F((-1 + F(7))) + ((4! × (3!)! + F(7)))
17438 := (((-1) × F(7)) × F(F((F(4)!)!)) + (F((F(F(3)) + (F(8))))))
17439 := (F((1 - (-7) × F(4))) + (F(3!) × (-F(9))))
17443 := (1 + (((7 + ((F(4)!)!) × 4!) - 3!))
17444 := (((1 × 7) + ((F(4)!)!) × 4!) - 4)
17447 := (-((1 - 74) × ((F(4)!)! + F(F(7))))
17448 := (((1 × 7) + ((F(4)!)!) × (F(4) × 8))
17454 := (((F(17) × 4) + 5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))
17464 := ((-1 + F(F(7))) + ((F(F(4)) - (6!)) × (-4!)))
17466 := ((1 - 7) + (4! × (F(6) + 6!)))
17469 := (((-((1 - 7)))! × 4!) + (F(F(6)) × 9))
17473 := (1 + (-7) × (4! - (7!/F(3))))
17479 := ((1 - F(F(7))) + F((4! + ((7 - 9))))
17480 := (((-1 - F(F(7))) + F(4)) + F((F(8) + 0!)))
17483 := (((-1 - F(F(7))) + (F(4)!) + F((F(8) + F(F(3))))))
17484 := ((-1 + F(7)) - (((F(4)!)! + 8) × (-4!)))
17486 := ((1 + F(7)) + (4! × (8 + 6!)))
17493 := ((17 × 49) × F(F(3!)))
17494 := (((-1) × F(7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) + ((9⁴))
17498 := (((-1 - F(F(7))) × ((F(4)!)! - F(9))) + F(F(8)))

$$\begin{aligned}17512 &:= ((-1 + F(F(7))) + ((5! \times F(12)))) \\17513 &:= ((F((-1 + F(7))) \times 5!) + (F(13))) \\17514 &:= ((1 + F(F(7))) + (((5 + 1)! \times 4!)) \\17524 &:= (-((1 - ((7^5) - 2))) + ((F(4))!)) \\17527 &:= (((1 \times 7)^5) + (-((F(2) - (7))))!) \\17534 &:= (((1 + (7^5)) + 3!!) + (F(4))!) \\17535 &:= (F((1 + 7)) \times ((-5) + 3!!) + 5!) \\17543 &:= (F((17 + 5)) - (F((F(4))!) \times F(F(3!)))) \\17544 &:= ((((-((1 - 7)))! + (5)) + (F(4))!) \times 4!) \\17545 &:= ((1 + F((7 + 5))) \times (F(F(F(4))) + 5!)) \\17546 &:= (F(F((1 + 7))) + (5! \times F((4 + 6)))) \\17547 &:= (((1 + (F(7) \times 5!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (7!)) \\17548 &:= (((((1 \times 7)^5) + ((F(4))!)) + (F(8))) \\17556 &:= ((1 - ((-7) \times 5!) + (5)) \times F(F(6))) \\17557 &:= (F(17) + (5! \times (5! + F(7)))) \\17578 &:= (((F(17) - (5)) + 7!) + F(F(8))) \\17579 &:= (((1 - F(7)) - 5!) + F((F(7) + 9))) \\17597 &:= (((-((1 - 7)) - 5!) + F((9 + F(7)))) \\17605 &:= (((1 + F(7)) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!))) - 5!) \\17606 &:= ((-1 - (F(7) \times F(6))) + F((0! + F(F(6)))) \\17608 &:= ((1 - (F(7) \times F(6))) + F((0! + F(8)))) \\17618 &:= (-1 + (((7!/6) - 1) \times F(8))) \\17619 &:= ((-1 + (7!/6)) \times F(-((1 - 9)))) \\17627 &:= ((((-1) \times 7!) + (F(6))!)/2) - F(7) \\17632 &:= ((1 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(F(6)) - F((F(3!) + 2)))) \\17633 &:= (1 + (((7! - (F(6))!)/(-F(3))) - F(3!)) \\17634 &:= (((((1 \times 7))! \times F(F(6)))/3!) - (F(4))! \\17635 &:= (((((1 \times 7))! \times F(F(6)))/3!) - (5)) \\17636 &:= (((1 - 7!) \times F(F(6))) + 3)/(-6) \\17637 &:= ((17 \times (F(F(6)) + 3!!)) + (7!)) \\17639 &:= (-1 - ((7!/F(6)) \times (3! - F(9)))) \\ \\17640 &:= 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 0 \\17641 &:= 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 1 \\17642 &:= 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 2\end{aligned}$$

$$17643 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 3$$

$$17644 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 4$$

$$17645 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 5$$

$$17646 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 6$$

$$17647 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 7$$

$$17648 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 8$$

$$17649 := 1 \times 7! \times F(F(6))/F(4)! + 9$$

$$17653 := (-1 + (7 \times ((F(F(6)) \times 5!) + F(3))))$$

$$17654 := ((1 \times 7) \times ((F(F(6)) \times 5!) + F(F(4))))$$

$$17657 := (17 + (F(F(6)) \times (5! \times 7)))$$

$$17660 := (((1 + (7!/6)) \times F(F(6))) - 0!)$$

$$17661 := ((1 + (7!/6)) \times F(F((6 \times 1))))$$

$$17662 := (((1 + (7!/6)) \times F(F(6))) + F(2))$$

$$17663 := (F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(6) \times 3!))$$

$$17664 := (((1 + 7) + F(6)) + 6!) \times 4!$$

$$17666 := (((F(F((1 + 7))) \times 6) + (F(6))!)/6)$$

$$17668 := (((1 - F(7)) - (F(6))!)/(-6) + F(F(8)))$$

$$17673 := (((1 + 7)!/6 + (7)) + F(F(F(3!))))$$

$$17674 := (F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(7) + 4!))$$

$$17683 := ((17 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((8!/3!)))$$

$$17684 := ((F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - (F(8))) - (F(4))!)$$

$$17690 := (F(((1 + F(7)) + F(6))) - F((9 - 0!)))$$

$$17703 := (F((F((1 + 7)) + ((7 \times 0)!)) - F(3!))$$

$$17704 := (-((F(F((1 + 7))) + 7)) + F(-((0! - 4!))))$$

$$17705 := (F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) - (0! + (5)))$$

$$17706 := (((1 + 7) - F(7)) + F((0! + F(F(6))))))$$

$$17707 := (-1 - ((-77) + 0!) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$17708 := ((F((1 + 7))/(-7)) + F((0! + F(8))))$$

$$17730 := ((-((1 - 7)) + F(7)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!)))$$

$$17731 := (((1 \times 7) + F(7)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1)))$$

$$17733 := ((1 + F(((F(7) + (7)) + F(3)))) + F(F(3!)))$$

$$17734 := ((-1 + F(((F(7) + (7)) + F(3)))) + (4!))$$

$$17735 := (F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (-((F(F(3)) - (5))))!$$

$$17739 := (F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) - ((3! - F(9)))$$

- 17740 := ((F((1 + F(7)))/F(7)) + F((F(F((F(4))!)) + 0!)))
- 17741 := ((17 + F(7)) + F((F(F((F(4))!)) + 1)))
- 17743 := (F((1 + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + (4 × F(3!)))
- 17744 := ((F((1 + 7)) + (F(7)^{F(4)})) × F((F(4))!))
- 17746 := ((F(F((1 × 7))) + F(F(7))) + (4! × 6!))
- 17760 := (((1 × 7) × 7) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!)))
- 17763 := (((-1 - F(F(7))) × (-76)) - F(F(3!)))
- 17764 := (((-1 - F(7)) × (F(F(7)) - (6!))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
- 17766 := (F((1 + 7)) × ((7!/6) + (6)))
- 17767 := ((((-1 + F(7)) + F(7)) × 6!) - F(F(7)))
- 17784 := (((((1 × 7))!/7) + F(8)) × 4!)
- 17814 := ((-1 - (F(7) × (-8))) + F((1 + F(F((F(4))!))))
- 17816 := ((F(17) × 8) + ((1 + 6)!))
- 17817 := (((F(17) × 8) + 1) + 7!)
- 17823 := (((1 + F(7)) × 8) + F((F(2) + F(F(3!))))
- 17825 := (((1 - 7) + F((F(8) + F(2)))) + 5!)
- 17830 := ((-1 + ((F(7) - 8)!)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!)))
- 17831 := (F(((1⁷) + F(8))) + ((3! - 1)!))
- 17832 := ((1 + ((F(7) - 8)!)) + F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))))
- 17834 := ((F((-1 + F(7))) - (F(8))) + F(-((F(3) - 4!))))
- 17835 := ((((-1 - 7!) + F(F(8))) × 3) + 5!)
- 17837 := (((F(17) × 8) + F(F(3!))) + (7!))
- 17843 := (-F(17)) + ((F(8) + (F(4))!) × (3!))
- 17845 := (((1 + F(7)) + F((F(8) + F(F(F(4))))) + 5!)
- 17853 := ((-1 + ((7!/F(8)) × 5!)) - F(F(F(3!))))
- 17864 := ((1 - F(F(7))) × (-F(8) - ((F(6))!/((F(4))!))))
- 17872 := ((-1 + F(F(7))) - ((8! - 7!)/(-2)))
- 17873 := (F(F((1 × 7))) + ((8! - 7!)/F(3)))
- 17874 := ((1 + F(F(7))) - (-((8! - 7!)/F(F(4))))
- 17924 := (((((1 + 7))!/(-9)) - F(2)) × (-4))
- 17934 := (((-1 + F(F(7))) - 9) + F(-((F(3) - 4!))))
- 17937 := (((1 + F((F(7) + 9))) - F(3!)) + F(F(7)))
- 17952 := ((1 + F((F(7) + 9))) - (5! × (-2)))
- 17975 := ((F((-1 + F(7))) + F((9 + F(7)))) + 5!)
- 17983 := ((-17) + (9!/F(8))) + 3!!

$$\begin{aligned}17986 &:= ((-1 - F(7)) + ((9!/F(8)) + 6!)) \\17987 &:= (((-((1 - 7)))! + ((9!/F(8)) - F(7))) \\17993 &:= (-((1 \times 7)) + ((F(9) - 9) \times (3!))) \\17994 &:= (((-((1 - 7)))! \times (F(9) - 9)) - (F(4)!)) \\17995 &:= (((-((1 - 7)))! \times (F(9) - 9)) - (5)) \\17999 &:= (-1 - (((F((F(7) - 9)))! \times (9 - F(9)))) \\18048 &:= ((-1 - (F((F(8) - 0!)/F(4))) \times (-8)) \\18064 &:= ((F(18) \times (0! + (6))) - 4!) \\18073 &:= (((F(18) - 0!) \times 7) - F(3!)) \\18074 &:= (((F(18) + 0!) \times 7) - F(F((F(4)!))) \\18081 &:= ((F(18) - 0!) \times (8 - 1)) \\18084 &:= -(((F(18) \times (0! - 8)) + (4))) \\18087 &:= ((-1 + F((F(8) + 0!))) + F((F(8) - (7)))) \\18088 &:= -((F(18) \times (((0 \times 8)! - 8))) \\18134 &:= (-1 + ((F((F(8) - 1)) - 3!!) \times F(4))) \\18136 &:= (((-(((1 + 8)!)/(1 - F(F(3!)))) - F(6)) \\18137 &:= (((F(18) + 1) + 3!) \times 7) \\18142 &:= (((-(((1 + 8)!)/(1 - F(F((F(4)!)))) - 2) \\18143 &:= (-1 - ((8! - F(((1 \times 4)!)) \times 3)) \\18146 &:= (((((1 + 8) + 1) \times ((F(4)!))! + F(F(F(6)))) \\18173 &:= (-1 - (F(F((8 - 1))) \times (-F(7) \times 3!))) \\18223 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) - (-2) \times (2^{F(3!)})) \\18244 &:= ((((-1 - F(F(8))) \times 2)/(-F(4))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\18264 &:= ((-1 + ((F(8) \times 2) + 6!)) \times 4!) \\18296 &:= -((F(18) - (29 \times 6!))) \\18315 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) - ((3! - F(15)))) \\18321 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + F(-((3! - (21)))) \\18322 &:= ((1 + F((F(8) - 3!))) + F(22)) \\18325 &:= ((F(-((1 - 8))) + 3!!) \times 25) \\18327 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + 3!) + F((2 + F(7)))) \\18330 &:= ((1 + F((F(8) - 3!))) \times 30) \\18333 &:= ((F(F(-((1 - 8)))) \times F(F(3!))) + ((F(3)!)/3)) \\18341 &:= (((-((1 - 8)!)/F(3!)) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 1))) \\18347 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + (-3) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - F(F(7)))) \\18354 &:= (((F((1 + 8)) + 3!!) + 5!) \times F(F((F(4)!)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18359 &:= (-1 + (((8!/F(F(3!))) + 5!) \times 9)) \\ 18376 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) - ((F((3 + 7)) - 6!))) \\ 18377 &:= (((F(18) + F(3!)) \times 7) + F(F(7))) \\ 18383 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + 3!!) - (8 \times 3!)) \\ 18386 &:= ((F(F((1 \times 8))) + 3!!) - (8!/(-6))) \\ 18389 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + 3!!) - (8 + F(9))) \\ 18393 &:= ((-1 - ((F(F(8)) \times F(3)) + F(9))) + (F(3!)!)) \\ 18394 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + 3!!) - (F(9) + F(4))) \\ 18396 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) - F(F(3))) - (F(9) - 6!)) \\ 18397 &:= ((-F((1 + 8))) + 3!!) + F((9 + F(7))) \\ 18406 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) - ((4! + 0!) - 6!)) \\ 18407 &:= ((((-1 + F(8)) \times 4) - 0!) \times F(F(7))) \\ 18413 &:= ((-18) + ((F(4)!)!) + F((1 + F(F(3!)))) \\ 18417 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4)!)!) - (1 + F(7))) \\ 18418 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4)!)!) - F(-(1 - 8))) \\ 18422 &:= ((-(1 + 8)) + ((F(4)!)!) + F(22)) \\ 18423 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) - (4 \times 2)) + 3!!) \\ 18424 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4)!)!) - (F(2) + (F(4)!)!)) \\ 18425 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) - (F(4)!)! + ((F(2) + (5)))!) \\ 18426 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + ((-4) - F(2)) + 6!) \\ 18427 &:= (-1 - ((F(F(8)) \times F(F(4))) - ((F(2) + (7))!)) \\ 18428 &:= (((1 - F(F(8))) \times F(F(4))) - (2 - 8!)) \\ 18429 &:= ((1 - (F(F(8)) \times F(F(4)))) + (-((F(2) - 9)))!)) \\ 18430 &:= (((F((1 + F(8))) - F(F(4))) + 3!!) + 0!) \\ 18431 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + (((4 + 3) - 1)!) \\ 18433 &:= (1 + (((8^{F(4)}) \times 3!) \times 3!)) \\ 18434 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + F(4)) + ((F(3) + (4))!)) \\ 18435 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4)^{3!}) - (5))) \\ 18437 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((3!)! + 7)) \\ 18438 &:= (((1 + F((F(8) - 4))) - 3!!) \times F(8)) \\ 18439 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((3!)! + 9)) \\ \\ 18440 &:= F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)}! + 0 \\ 18441 &:= F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)}! + 1 \\ 18442 &:= F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)}! + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$18443 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 3$$

$$18444 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 4$$

$$18445 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 5$$

$$18446 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 6$$

$$18447 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 7$$

$$18448 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 8$$

$$18449 := F(1 + F(8)) + F(4)^{F(4)!} + 9$$

$$18452 := ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4))!)) + F(F(((5 - 2))!)))$$

$$18453 := ((18 \times (4^5)) + F(F(3!)))$$

$$18454 := (((F(F(-(1 - 8)))) - F(4!)) / (-5)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$18455 := ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4))!)) + (5!/5))$$

$$18462 := ((F((1 + 8)) + (F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-2)))$$

$$18463 := ((F((1 + F(8))) + (4! + F(6))) + 3!!)$$

$$18464 := (F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4)^6 + 4!))$$

$$18467 := (F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4)!/F(6) - (7!)))$$

$$18469 := (F((1 + F(8))) + ((4 + 6!) + F(9)))$$

$$18472 := (-1 + (F((8 + (F(4))!)) \times (7^2)))$$

$$18473 := (-1 + (((8!/F(4)) + 7!) - 3!))$$

$$18474 := (((((1 \times 8))!/F(4)) + 7!) - (F(4))!)$$

$$18475 := (((((1 \times 8))!/F(4)) + 7!) - (5))$$

$$18480 := (((-(1 - 8))!/F(4))! \times (F(8) + 0!))$$

$$18481 := (1 + ((8!/F(4)) + ((8 - 1))!))$$

$$18483 := (((-(1 - 8))! + ((F(4) + (8!/3))))$$

$$18484 := (((-(1 - 8))! - (-4 - (8!/F(4))))$$

$$18486 := ((18 \times F((4! - 8))) + (6!))$$

$$18487 := (-1 + (((8!/F(4)) + 8) + 7!))$$

$$18499 := ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(4))!)) + (F(9) + F(9)))$$

$$18535 := ((1 + (8!/5!)) \times F((F(3) \times 5)))$$

$$18536 := ((F(((1 + F(8)) - (5))) + 3!!) \times F(6))$$

$$18537 := (F((1 + F(8))) + ((5! - F(3)) \times 7))$$

$$18543 := (((F((1 + F(8))) + 5!) - F((F(4))!)) + ((3)!))$$

$$18546 := ((1 + F(8)) \times ((5! + F(4)) + 6!))$$

$$18548 := (((((1 \times 8))! + 5!) - (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}18551 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + ((5! + ((5 + 1))!))) \\18556 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + ((5! + (5)) + 6!)) \\18563 &:= (-1 + ((F(8) + (5)) \times (6! - 3!))) \\18564 &:= ((F((1 \times 8)) + (5)) \times (6! - (F(4))!)) \\18573 &:= ((-1 - F(F(8))) - (((5! - 7!) \times 3!))) \\18574 &:= ((-1) \times F(F(8))) - ((5! - 7!) \times (F(4))!) \\18577 &:= ((F((18 + 5)) - 7!) - 7!) \\18584 &:= (((-((1 - 8)))! \times (-5)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-4))) \\18625 &:= ((-1 + F(F(8))) + (((F(6)^2) \times 5!)) \\18639 &:= (-1 - ((F((F(8) - F(6))) \times (3!)!)/(-9))) \\18640 &:= ((F(F(-((1 - 8)))) \times 6!)/(F((F(4))! + 0!)) \\18642 &:= (F(-((1 - 8))) \times ((6! - F(4)) \times 2)) \\18647 &:= (-1 + (F(8) \times (6! + (4! \times 7)))) \\18648 &:= (((F((1 \times 8)) \times F(6)) + ((F(4))!)! \times F(8)) \\18656 &:= ((1 + F(8)) \times ((F(6) + 5!) + 6!)) \\18664 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + F((F(F(6)) - F(6)))) + ((F(4))!)!) \\18665 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + (-6 + (F(6) \times 5!))) \\18675 &:= -((F((-1 + F(8))) - ((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times (-5!))) \\18677 &:= (((F((1 + F(8))) + (6!)) + F(F(7))) + F(7)) \\18694 &:= ((-((1^8)) + 6!) \times (F(9) - F((F(4))!))) \\18695 &:= ((-F((1 + 8))) - (F(6))!) + (9^5) \\18698 &:= ((-1 - F(8)) + (6! \times (F(9) - 8))) \\18720 &:= ((F(-((1 - 8))) + F(7)) \times (((2 + 0!)!)!) \\18733 &:= (F(-((1 - 8))) + ((F(7) \times F(3)) \times (3!)!)) \\18734 &:= ((-((1 - 8)) - (-F(7)) \times (3!)!) \times F(F(4))) \\18742 &:= ((1 + F(8)) + ((-F(7)) \times ((F(4))!)!) \times (-2)) \\18743 &:= ((F((1 + F(8))) + ((F(7) \times 4!))) + 3!) \\18744 &:= (((F(18) - F(F(7))) - F((F(4))!) \times F((F(4))!)) \\18745 &:= (((F(-((1 - 8))) \times F(F(7))) + ((F(4))!)!) \times 5) \\18746 &:= ((F(-((1 - 8))) + F(7)) \times (F(F(F(4))) + (6!))) \\18759 &:= (F(-((1 - 8))) \times (F(7) \times (5! - 9))) \\18762 &:= ((F((1 \times 8)) + (F(7) \times 6!)) \times 2) \\18763 &:= (1 + ((F(8) + (F(7) \times 6!)) \times F(3))) \\18764 &:= (((1 + F(8)) + (F(7) \times 6!)) \times F(F(4))) \\18784 &:= (((F(18) - F(F(7))) \times 8) - (4!))\end{aligned}$$

- 18808** := $((F(18) - F(F((8 - 0!)))) \times 8)$
18824 := $(F(-((1 - 8))) \times (8 - (-2) \times ((F(4))!)))$
18834 := $(((-1 + F((8 + 8))) \times F(3!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
18843 := $((-((1 - 8)))! - (F(8) - (4!^3)))$
18844 := $((-((F(18) - 8!)) / F(F(4))) - (4!))$
18864 := $(-(((F(18) - 8!) + F(6))) / F(F(4)))$
18865 := $((-1 + F(F(8))) - ((8! - 6!) / (-5)))$
18868 := $((F(18) - 8!) / (6 - 8))$
18884 := $((((18 \times F(8)) \times F(8)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
18926 := $((F((1 \times 8)))! / ((9 \times 2)!) + F(F(F(6))))$
18936 := $((F(18) \times 9) - (3! \times 6!))$
18943 := $((F((-1 + F(8))) + F(9)) - (-((4!)! / (F(F(3))!)))$
18944 := $((F(18) + (-9 \times 4!)) \times F((F(4))!))$
18954 := $((18 \times 9) \times (5! - F(4)))$
18967 := $(((((1 \times 8))! + 9!) / F(F(6))) - F(F(7)))$
19039 := $(-1 - ((-F(9)) \times ((0! + 3!)!) / 9))$
19164 := $((F(19) - F(16)) \times (F(4))!)$
19237 := $(1 - ((-((F(9)^2)) \times F(F(3!))) + (7!)))$
19284 := $((F(19) \times 2) + F(F(8))) - (4!))$
19294 := $(-((F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + ((-2) \times 9!) / 4!))$
19324 := $((F(19) + F(3!)) \times 2) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))$
19337 := $(-1 + ((F(9) \times ((3!)! - 3)) - (7!)))$
19343 := $(-1 + ((F(9) - F(3!)) \times (4! + 3!)))$
19344 := $((F(F(-((1 - 9)))) + 3!) \times (F(4))! - F(4!))$
19346 := $(((((1 + F(9)) \times (3!)!) / F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
19362 := $((1 - F((F(9) / F(3)))) + (F(6))!) / 2$
19364 := $(F(19) + (F(F(3!)) \times (6! + F(4))))$
19372 := $((F(F(-((1 - 9)))) \times F(3)) + (7! / (-2)))$
19407 := $(1 + ((F(9) \times (((F(4))!)! - 0!)) - (7!)))$
19413 := $((1 \times 9) \times F(4)) \times (-1 + 3!))$
19414 := $(1 + (9 \times (((F(4))!)! - 1) \times F(4)))$
19415 := $(F((1 + 9)) \times (F(F(((F(4))! + 1)))) + 5!))$
19423 := $((F((1 \times 9)) - (F((F(4))!)!) / (-2)) - ((3!)!))$
19424 := $(1 + (((F(9) - (F((F(4))!)!) / (-2)) - (((F(4))!)!)))$
19430 := $(-1 - (9 \times ((-F(4)) \times (3!)! + 0!)))$

- 19431** := $((1 \times 9) \times ((F(4) \times (3!)!) - 1))$
19432 := $(1 - (9 \times ((-F(4)) \times (3!)!) + F(2)))$
19433 := $(1 - (((-9) \times F(4)) \times (3!)!) + F(3!))$
19434 := $(((((1 \times 9) \times F(4)) \times (3!)!) - (F(4))!)$
19435 := $(((((1 \times 9) \times F(4)) \times (3!)!) - (5))$
19436 := $((((-((-((1 - 9)))!) + F((F(4))!)))/(-F(3))) - (6!))$
19437 := $((-1 + F(9)) \times ((4!^{F(3)} + F(7)))$
19439 := $(-1 - (((9 - F(4)))! \times -(3 \times 9)))$
- 19440** := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 0$
19441 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 1$
19442 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 2$
19443 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 3$
19444 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 4$
19445 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 5$
19446 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 6$
19447 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 7$
19448 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 8$
19449 := $1 \times 9 \times F(4) \times F(4)!! + 9$
- 19456** := $((19 \times F((F(4))!)) \times (5! + F(6)))$
19463 := $(-1 + (((9 \times ((F(4))!)) + F(6)) \times 3))$
19464 := $(((((1 \times 9) \times F(4)) \times 6!) + 4!)$
19466 := $(-1 - (((-9!) - F(4!))/F(F(6))) + F(F(6))))$
19467 := $(((((1 - F(9)) + ((F(4))!)) \times F(F(6))) + (7!))$
19468 := $(1 - (((-9!) - F(4!))/F(F(6))) + (F(8)))$
19473 := $((19 \times F((F(4) + F(7)))) + 3!)$
19474 := $((F((1 \times 9)) - ((F(4))!)) + (7! \times 4))$
19483 := $(1 - (((9! + F(4!))/(-F(8))) + 3!))$
19484 := $((((-1) \times 9!) - F(4!))/(-F(8))) - 4$
19486 := $(-1 - (((-9!) - F(4!)) + (F(8)))/F(F(6)))$
19487 := $(-1 - ((9! + F(4!))/(-8 - F(7))))$
19488 := $(((((1 \times 9))! + F((F(4) \times 8)))/F(8))$
19494 := $((19^{F(F(4))} \times 9) \times (F(4))!)$
19496 := $(-((1 - 9)) + ((F(4!) + 9!)/F(F(6))))$

- 19498 := $((1 + 9) + ((F(4!) + 9!)/F(8)))$
19535 := $((F(19) \times (-5)) + (F(3!)!) + 5!)$
19536 := $((-1 + F(9)) \times ((-5!) + 3!!) - F(6))$
19548 := $((F(19) + 5!) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(8))$
19555 := $((-1 + (F(9) \times (5 - 5!))) \times (-5))$
19557 := $(-1 + ((F(9) + 5!) \times (5! + (7))))$
19567 := $((1 - F(9)) \times (5! - 6!)) - F(F(7))$
19573 := $(1 + ((-(9 + 5)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-3!))$
19586 := $((1 \times 9) \times 5!) \times 8 + F(F(F(6)))$
19604 := $(F(19) + 6!) \times 04$
19631 := $((-(1 - 9))! / F(F(6))) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1))$
19635 := $((1 + F(9)) \times ((F(F(6))^{F(3)}) + 5!))$
19643 := $(F(19) + (6)) + (F(4!)/3)$
19644 := $(F(19) - ((F(F(6)) + F(4!)) / (-F(4))))$
19648 := $((1 - 9) \times F((-6) + 4!)) + 8!$
19655 := $(-1 - (((F(9) - (6))!) / (-((5 \times 5)!)))$
19664 := $((-1 + F(9)) \times 6!) - (F(6)^4)$
19677 := $(-1 + ((F(9) \times (6! + (7))) - 7!))$
19685 := $(-1 + (F(9) \times ((6! - F(8)) - 5!)))$
19695 := $((1 + (9!/6!)) \times (F(9) + (5)))$
19740 := $((-F(19)) + F(F(7))) \times (-4 - 0!)$
19741 := $(1 + (F((9 + 7)) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - 1)))$
19760 := $((1 + F((9 + 7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!))$
19783 := $-((F((1^9) + F(7))) - (8!/F(3)))$
19794 := $((1 - (-97) \times F(9)) \times (F(4)!))$
19833 := $((-1 + F(9)) + ((8! - 3!)/F(3)))$
19834 := $(F((1 \times 9)) - ((-8!) + 3!)/F(F(4)))$
19863 := $(-1 + ((9!/F(8)) + F((6 \times 3))))$
19864 := $(F(((1 + 9) + 8)) + (6! \times 4!))$
19894 := $((-(1 - 9)) + F(8)) \times (-F(9)) + ((F(4)!))!$
19927 := $((1 \times 9)! / (9 \times 2)) - F(F(7))$
19936 := $((19 + 9) \times ((3!)! - F(6)))$
19944 := $((-1 + F((9 + 9))) \times F((F(4)!)) - ((F(4)!))!$
19993 := $(-F(19)) - (F(9) \times (9 - 3!))$
20076 := $((2 + 0!) + 0!) \times (7! - F(F(6)))$

- 20143 := ((F((F((2 + 0!)!) + 1)) - (F((F(4)!)!)) / (-F(3)))
- 20147 := ((((((2 + 0!)! + 1))! × 4) - F(7))
- 20152 := -((F(((2 + 0!)!)) - ((F((1 + 5)))! / 2)))
- 20154 := -((((2 + 0!)! - ((F((1 + 5)))! / F(F(4))))))
- 20155 := (((F(((2 + 0!)!)!)) / F(F(-(1 - 5)))) - (5))
- 20160 := (((2 + 0!) + 1) × ((F(6) - 0!)!))
- 20163 := (((((2 + 0!)! + (F((1 × 6)))!)) / F(3))
- 20167 := ((F((20 - 1)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (7!))
- 20176 := (2 × (((0! + 1) × 7!) + F(6)))
- 20182 := (F(F(((2 + 0!)!)) - (-1 - (8! / 2)))
- 20223 := ((F(20) - ((2 + 2)!) × 3)
- 20224 := (((F(((2 + 0!)!)!)) / 2) + (2^{F(4)!}))
- 20232 := ((F((2 × ((0! + 2)!)!)) + (F(3!)!)) / 2)
- 20244 := ((-(((F(2) + ((0! + 2)!)!)) - F(F((F(4)!)!))) × (-4))
- 20249 := (((F(((2 + 0!)!)!)) / 2) + F((F(F(4)) + 9)))
- 20265 := (((F(((2 + 0!)!)!)) / 2) + (F(F(6)) × 5))
- 20286 := (F(F(((2 + 0!)!)) × (F((2 × 8)) - F(F(6))))
- 20293 := (-2) - (F((-0! + F(-(F(2) - 9)))) × (-3))
- 20294 := (-F(2)) - (F((-0! + F(-(F(2) - 9)))) × (-F(4)))
- 20303 := ((F(20) × 3) + F((03)!))
- 20306 := ((((((2 + 0!)!)! × F((3! + 0!))) + F(F(F(6))))
- 20307 := (((F(20) × 3) - 0!) + F(7))
- 20308 := ((F(20) × 3) + F(-(0! - 8)))
- 20313 := ((F(20) + 3!) × (1 × 3))
- 20329 := (((F(20) × 3!) / 2) + F(9))
- 20334 := ((F(20) + F((F(F(3)) + 3!))) × F(4))
- 20335 := ((F(20) × 3) + (F(3!) × 5))
- 20337 := ((F(20) × 3) - (3! × (-7)))
- 20343 := ((F(20) × 3) + (4! × F(3)))
- 20349 := (((F(20) / 3) + (F(4)!) × 9)
- 20358 := ((-F(20)) - F(F(3!))) × (5 - 8))
- 20363 := (203 + ((F(6)!) / F(3)))
- 20373 := ((F(20) × 3) + (F(7) × 3!))
- 20393 := (((F(((2 + 0!)!)!)) / F(3)) + F(F((9 - F(3))))))
- 20395 := ((F(2) - (((0! - 3!)! × F(9))) × (-5))

- 20396 := $(2 \times (((0! + F(F(3!))) \times (-F(9))) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 20403 := $((((2 + 0!))!)! + ((F(4)^{0!+F(3!)}))$
- 20415 := $((F(20) \times F(4)) + ((1 \times 5))!)$
- 20432 := $(-(20) + (((F(4))!)! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-2))$
- 20433 := $((2 \times ((0! - ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(F(3!))))$
- 20434 := $((-(((2 + 0!)^{F(4)!}) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(F(4)))$
- 20436 := $(2 \times ((0! - (F(4)^{3!}) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 20437 := $((2 \times ((-(0!) - ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(7))$
- 20438 := $(2 \times (((-(0!) - (F(4))!) - 3!!) + F(F(8))))$
- 20444 := $((F(F(F(((2 + 0!)!)))) - (4 + ((F(4))!)!) \times F(F(4)))$
- 20445 := $(F(20) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-(4! - 5))))$
- 20446 := $(2 \times (((0 - ((F(4))!)!) - F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 20447 := $((2 \times ((0! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (((F(4))!)!)) - 7)$
- 20448 := $((20 \times ((F(4))!)!) + ((F(4!) - 8!))$
- 20450 := $(2 \times ((-(0!) - ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F((5 + 0!))))))$
- 20452 := $((((2 + 0!)! - F(F((F(4) + 5)))) \times (-2))$
- 20454 := $F(20) + ((F(4) - 5!)^{F(F(4))})$
- 20455 := $((((F(((2 + 0!)!)^4) - 5)) \times 5)$
- 20463 := $((F(20) \times F(4)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(3!)))$
- 20464 := $((((2 + 0!)! - ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(F(4)))$
- 20466 := $(2 \times (((-(0!) - ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(6))$
- 20467 := $((2 \times ((0! - ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(7))$
- 20468 := $(2 \times (F((F(04))!) - (6! - F(F(8))))))$
- 20475 := $(-(F(20)) - (((F(4))! - F(F(7))) \times 5!))$
- 20476 := $(2 \times (((-(0!) - ((F(4))!)!) + F(7)) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 20478 := $(2 \times ((0 - ((F(4))!)!) + (F(7) + F(F(8))))))$
- 20480 := $((2^{F(F(04)!)} \times 80)$
- 20493 := $((((F(20) - F((F(4))!)) \times 9) - (F(3!))!)$
- 20535 := $((((F(20) + 5!) \times 3) - 5!)$
- 20546 := $((((-(20) \times 5!) \times (-4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
- 20598 := $((2 + 0!) \times (-(5! \times F(9))) + F(F(8))))$
- 20639 := $((2 + (F(06))!) - ((3^9))$
- 20643 := $((F((2 \times F(06))) - 4) \times F(F(3!)))$
- 20647 := $((((2 + 0!)! + (((F(6))! / F(F(4))) - F(F(7))))$

- 20648 := (((-2) - 0!) + F((-6) + 4!)) × 8)
- 20653 := (-2) - ((F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) + 5!) × (-3))
- 20654 := -(F(2)) - ((F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) + 5!) × (-F(4)))
- 20656 := ((-2) + F((F(0! + (6))) + (5)))) × F(6)
- 20664 := (((20 + F(F(6))) × F(F(6))) × 4!)
- 20666 := ((F(((2 + 0!) × 6)) × F(6)) - 6)
- 20672 := (F(((2 + 0!) × 6)) × (7 + F(2)))
- 20673 := (F(2) + (F(-(((0! - (6)) - F(7)))) × F(3!)))
- 20674 := (2 + (F(-(((0! - (6)) - F(7)))) × F((F(4))!)))
- 20675 := ((2 + 0!) + (F(6) × F((F(7) + (5)))))
- 20687 := ((2 × ((0! - 6!) + F(F(8)))) + F(F(7)))
- 20693 := (F(F(((2 + 0!)!)) - (-F(6) × F((9 × F(3)))))
- 20706 := ((F(((2 + 0!) + F(7))) - 0!) × F(F(6)))
- 20726 := (-F(2) + (F((0! + (7))) × F((2 × F(6)))))
- 20727 := (F(((2 + 0!) + F(7))) × F((F(2) + (7))))
- 20728 := ((F(((2 + 0!) + F(7)))² - 8)
- 20729 := (2 + ((F(-((0! - F(7))))² - 9))
- 20732 := (-2) + ((F(-((0! - F(7))))^{F(3)} - 2))
- 20733 := ((F(((2 + 0!) + F(7)))^{F(3)} - 3)
- 20734 := (-2) + (((0! + F(7)) - F(3))⁴)
- 20736 := (((-2) + 0!) + F(7))^{-F(3)+6})
- 20737 := (F((-2) + F(07)) × F((3! + (7))))
- 20740 := (F((2 + F(07))) × F((F((F(4))!) + 0!)))
- 20742 := (((2 + 0!)! + (F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))))²))
- 20743 := F(2) + (0! - F(7))⁴ + 3!
- 20744 := 2 + (0! - F(7))⁴ + F(4)!
- 20745 := (F(((2 + 0!)!)) + (F(F(7)) × F(((F(4))! + (5)))))
- 20746 := 2 + (0! - F(7))⁴ + F(6)
- 20747 := (-F(2)) - ((0! - F((-7) + 4!)) × F(7))
- 20764 := ((2 + 0!) - (-F(7) × F((F(F(6)) - 4))))
- 20766 := (((2 + 0!)! × (F((F(7) + (6))) - (6!)))
- 20769 := (F(((2 + 0!)!)) - (-F(7) × F((F(6) + 9))))
- 20784 := (((-2 + A2041) × (07)!) + F(F(8))) × 4!
- 20846 := ((((((2 + 0!)!))! - 8!)/(-4)) + F(F(F(6))))

$$20853 := (((((2 + 0!))!) + F((F(8) - (5)))) \times F(F(3!)))$$

$$20867 := (((((2 + 0!))!)! \times (F(8) + F(6))) - F(7))$$

$$20874 := ((F((2 \times 08)) + (7)) \times F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$20880 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 0$$

$$20881 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 1$$

$$20882 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 2$$

$$20883 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 3$$

$$20884 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 4$$

$$20885 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 5$$

$$20886 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 6$$

$$20887 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 7$$

$$20888 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 8$$

$$20889 := (2 + 0!)!! \times (8 + F(8)) + 9$$

$$20905 := (F((20 - ((9 \times 0))!)) \times 5)$$

$$20916 := (F(F(((2 + 0!)!)) \times (9 + F(16)))$$

$$20935 := ((F((-2) + F(-(0! - 9)))) + 3!) \times 5)$$

$$20943 := ((F(20) - (-9 \times 4!)) \times 3)$$

$$20944 := (F(((2 + 0!)!)) \times (F(9) + F((F(4) \times (F(4))!))))$$

$$20945 := ((F((-2) + F(-(0! - 9)))) + F((F(4))!)) \times 5)$$

$$20948 := ((2 + ((0! + 9)^4)) + F(F(8)))$$

$$20979 := ((F(2) + ((0! + 9) \times F(F(7)))) \times 9)$$

$$21026 := ((((((2 + 1))! + 0!)! \times 2) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$21027 := ((F(21) + 0!) - (-2 \times 7!))$$

$$21063 := (((2^{10}) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(3!)))$$

$$21172 := -((((2 + 1))!)! + (F(F((1 + 7))) \times (-2)))$$

$$21174 := ((2 \times (1 + F(F((1 + 7)))))) - ((F(4))!)$$

$$21184 := (((2^{11}) + 8!) / F(F(4)))$$

$$21338 := (2 \times (((1 + F(F(3!)))^3) + (F(8))))$$

$$21344 := (2 \times (((1 + F(F(3!)))^{F(4)}) + (4!)))$$

$$21346 := ((2 + ((1 + F(3!))!)) / (-4 + F(F(6))))$$

$$21348 := (-2 \times ((F((1 + F(3!))) \times F((F(4))!)) - F(F(8))))$$

$$21378 := (2 \times ((-(((1 + 3))!) - F(F(7))) + F(F(8))))$$

$$21384 := (2 \times ((-F(13)) + F(F(8))) - F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21392 &:= (((2+1)!)! - (F(3!) \times (-F((9 \times 2)))) \\ 21424 &:= ((2^{14}) + ((F(2) + (F(4)!)!)) \\ 21428 &:= (2 \times ((1 - F(F((F(4)!) + F(2)))) + F(F(8)))) \\ 21434 &:= (-2) \times ((F(F((1 + (F(4)!)!))) - F(F(F(3!)))) - 4) \\ 21436 &:= (((-F(2)) - F((1 + 4!))) \times (-3!)) / F(F(6)) \\ 21438 &:= (-2) \times (F(F((1 + (F(4)!)!))) - (3! + F(F(8)))) \\ 21447 &:= ((F(((2+1)!)!))! + (-((F(4)^4) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 21454 &:= (-F(21)) - (-45) \times ((F(4)!)!)) \\ 21457 &:= (((2+1)!)! + (F((F(4)!) + 5))) \times F(F(7)) \\ 21468 &:= (-2) \times (F(F((1 + (F(4)!)!))) - (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) \\ 21474 &:= (((F(21) + 4!) - F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))) \\ 21476 &:= (2 \times (((1 + 4!) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 21494 &:= (2 \times (-((F(F((1 + (F(4)!)!))) - F(9))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) \\ 21496 &:= (2 \times (((1 + F(F((F(4)!)!))) \times (-9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 21532 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + ((3!)! / (-2))) \\ 21538 &:= (2 \times ((1 + 5!) \times F((3 + 8)))) \\ 21564 &:= (-(((2+1)!) - (5 \times 6!))) \times (F(4)!) \\ 21598 &:= (-2) - (((1 + 5)!) \times (-9 - F(8))) \\ 21604 &:= (2 \times (-F((F((1 + 6)) - 0!))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) \\ 21625 &:= (((2+1)!)! - (F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times (-5))) \\ 21630 &:= ((F(2) + ((1 \times 6)!) \times 30) \\ 21632 &:= (2 \times ((F((1 + 6)) \times F(3!)^2)) \\ 21634 &:= ((2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(3)^{F(F(4)!)}) \\ 21635 &:= ((F(2) + ((1 + 6!) \times 3!)) \times 5) \\ 21638 &:= (2 \times (-1 + ((F(F(6)) \times (-3!)) + F(F(8)))) \\ 21644 &:= (2 \times ((-((-((1 - 6)!)! + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) - 4)) \\ 21646 &:= ((-F(21)) + (F(6)!) - (F(4)! / 6)) \\ 21648 &:= (-2) \times (((-((1 - 6)!)! + F(F(4))) - F(F(8)))) \\ \\ 21650 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 0 \\ 21651 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 1 \\ 21652 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 2 \\ 21653 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 3 \\ 21654 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 4 \\ 21655 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21656 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 6 \\
 21657 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 7 \\
 21658 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 8 \\
 21659 &:= 2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(6))) - 5!) + 9 \\
 \\
 21664 &:= (2 \times ((-((-((1 - 6)))!) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4))!)) \\
 21668 &:= (-2) \times (((-((1 - 6)))! - F(6)) - F(F(8))) \\
 21678 &:= (-2) \times (((-((1 - 6)))! - F(7)) - F(F(8))) \\
 21684 &:= (2 \times ((F((1 + 6)) \times (-8)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 21714 &:= (F((2 \times (1 + 7))) \times (1 + F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 21723 &:= ((F(21) - (F(7)^2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 21734 &:= (2 \times ((-1 - (F(7) \times 3!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 21736 &:= (2 \times (((-1) \times F(7)) \times 3!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 21738 &:= (2 \times ((1 - (F(7) \times 3!)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 21746 &:= (F(21) - ((F(7) + F(F(4))) \times (-6!))) \\
 21765 &:= (((F(21) - 7) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5!) \\
 21772 &:= ((2 \times F(F((1 + 7)))) - (((7 - 2))!)) \\
 21785 &:= (((F(21) + F(7)) + F(F(8))) - 5!) \\
 21834 &:= (((F(21) - F(8)) - F(3!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 21836 &:= (2 \times (((-1 + F(F(8))) - 3!) - F(F(6)))) \\
 21838 &:= (2 \times (F(F((1 \times 8))) - (3! + F(8)))) \\
 21840 &:= (2 \times ((-1 + F(F(8))) - (4! + 0!))) \\
 21841 &:= ((2 \times ((-1 + F(F(8))) - (4!))) - 1) \\
 21843 &:= (F(2) + (((-1 + F(F(8))) - (4!)) \times F(3))) \\
 21844 &:= ((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - ((4! + 4!))) \\
 21850 &:= ((F(21) - F(8)) \times F(F((5 - 0!))) \\
 21852 &:= (2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - F(F(((5 - 2))!))) \\
 21854 &:= (2 \times (F(F((1 \times 8))) - (-5 + 4!))) \\
 21860 &:= ((2 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) - F((F(6) + 0!))) \\
 21863 &:= (((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - F(F(6))) - F(3!)) \\
 21870 &:= (2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - (F(7) - 0!))) \\
 21873 &:= ((2 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) - (F(7) + 3!)) \\
 21876 &:= (2 \times ((-1 + F(F(8))) - (7!/6!))) \\
 21880 &:= (2 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) - (8 - 0!))) \\
 21884 &:= (((-(((2 + 1))!) + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) - F(F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21889 &:= (((((2+1))! + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) - 9) \\21896 &:= -((F((2 \times (1+8))) - (F(9) \times 6!))) \\21904 &:= ((-(((2+1))!) - F(F((9-0!)))) \times (-F(F(4)))) \\21906 &:= (2 \times (F(F(-(1-9)))) + (0! + (6))) \\21907 &:= ((2 \times (1 + F(F((9-0!)))))) + F(7) \\21910 &:= ((F(21) + 9) \times (1 + 0!)) \\21914 &:= ((2 \times (-1 + F(F((9-1)))))) + (4!) \\21923 &:= ((-((2+1)) + F(9)) - (-2) \times F(F(F(3!)))) \\ \\21930 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 0) \\21931 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 1) \\21932 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 2) \\21933 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 3) \\21934 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 4) \\21935 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 5) \\21936 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 6) \\21937 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 7) \\21938 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 8) \\21939 &:= 2 \times (19 + F(F(F(3!))) + 9) \\ \\21940 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 0) \\21941 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 1) \\21942 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 2) \\21943 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 3) \\21944 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 4) \\21945 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 5) \\21946 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 6) \\21947 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 7) \\21948 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 8) \\21949 &:= 2 \times (F(F(-1+9)) + 4!) + 9) \\ \\21952 &:= (-(((2+1))! - F(9)))^{5-2} \\21958 &:= (2 \times ((-1 + F(9)) + F(F(F((-(5-8))!)))))) \\21983 &:= ((2 \times ((1 + F(9)) + F(F(8)))) + F(F(3!))) \\21984 &:= ((2 \times (F((1 \times 9)) + F(F(8)))) + (4!)) \\22036 &:= (F((2 \times ((2+0!)!)) - (-F(3) \times F(F(F(6))))))\end{aligned}$$

- 22084** := $((2 \times F(F(F((2 + 0!)))))) + (8 \times 4!))$
- 22096** := $(2 \times (((2 + 0!) \times F(9)) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 22132** := $(2 \times (F(21) + ((3 + 2)!))$
- 22133** := $(F(2) - (2 \times (-(((-1 + 3!))!) - F(F(F(3!))))))$
- 22134** := $(2 \times ((F(2) + ((-1 + 3!))!) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))))$
- 22136** := $(2 \times ((2 + ((-1 + 3!))!) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 22137** := $((2 \times (F(21) + 3!)) + F(F(7)))$
- 22144** := $(2 \times (F(21) + ((F(4))! \times F(F((F(4))!))))))$
- 22148** := $((2^{F((2+1)!)} + (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))))$
- 22153** := $((2 \times (F(21) + 5!)) + F(F(3!)))$
- 22244** := $(2 \times ((22 \times F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))))$
- 22314** := $((((F((2 + 2)))!)! \times 31) - (F(4))!)$
- 22315** := $((((F((2 + 2)))!)! \times 31) - (5))$
- 22320** := $((((F((2 + 2)))!)! \times (32 - 0!))$
- 22332** := $(-(F(2)) + ((2 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(F(3!))²))))$
- 22333** := $((2 \times F(F(2³))) + (F(F(3!))^{F(3)}))$
- 22334** := $(F(2) - ((-2) \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))}))$
- 22337** := $-((F(F((F((2 + 2)))!)) + (-F(3)) \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))))))$
- 22344** := $((F(2) + (F(F((F(2) + 3!))) \times (-4))) \times (-4!))$
- 22346** := $(2 \times ((F(F((F(2) + 3!))) - (F(4))!) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 22347** := $((((F((F((2 + 2)))!)!)/F(3)) + (F(4)⁷))$
- 22349** := $(-(2) + ((-F(2)) - 3!!) \times (F(4) - F(9)))$
- 22354** := $(2 \times ((-2) + F(F(F(3!)))) + F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))$
- 22360** := $(2 \times ((F(F((F(2) + 3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0!))$
- 22362** := $(((2 + F(F((F(2) + 3!)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 2)$
- 22364** := $(2 \times ((F(F((F(2) + 3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4)))$
- 22366** := $((2 \times (F(F((F(2) + 3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(6))$
- 22367** := $(-(F(2)) + (((2 \times 3!) \times F(6)) \times F(F(7))))$
- 22368** := $2^{2+3} \times (6! - F(8))$
- 22373** := $((-F(22)) + (F(3!))!) - (F(F(7)) + 3)$
- 22374** := $((F(2) - ((-2) \times F(3!)) \times F(F(7)))) \times (F(4))!$
- 22376** := $((-F(22)) - F((3! + 7))) + (F(6))!$
- 22378** := $((-((F(22) - F(3))) - F(F(7))) + 8!)$
- 22383** := $((2 \times ((2^{F(3!)} + F(F(8)))) - F(F(3!)))$

- 22388 := $(2 \times (((2^{F(3!)}) - 8) + F(F(8))))$
 22394 := $(-(2) + ((2 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (-9!)/((F(4))!)))$
 22395 := $((F(2) + ((2^3)!/(-9))) \times (-5))$
 22396 := $((2 \times F(F(2^3))) + ((9!/6!)))$
 22404 := $(2 \times ((2^{F(F(4)!)}) + F(F(F((F(04))!))))$
 22406 := $(2 \times (((2^{F(F(4)!)}) + 0!) + F(F(F(6))))$
 22434 := $((22 \times F((4^{F(3)}))) + ((F(4))!))$
 22436 := $(2 \times ((F((F(2) + F((F(4))!))) \times F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
 22437 := $(-(F(2)) - (-2) \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (F(F(3!)) \times F(7))))$
 22438 := $(2 \times ((F((F(2) + (F(4))!)) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(8))))$
 22442 := $((-22) - ((F(4))!)) + (F(4!)/2)$
 22443 := $((F(((2+2)!)/F(F(4))) - ((F(4))!)) - F(F(3!)))$
 22446 := $(2 \times (((2^{F(F(4)!)}) + F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F(F(6))))$
 22456 := $(2 \times ((2 \times (F(F((F(4))!)) + 5!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
 22462 := $((F(((2+2)!)/F(F(4))) - ((6! + 2)))$
 22463 := $((F(((2+2)!)/F(F(4))) - (6!)) - F(F(3)))$
 22464 := $((F((2+2))!)^{F(4)} + (6!)) \times 4!$
 22465 := $((-(F(22) + 4!)) + (F(6))! - 5!)$
 22466 := $((((2+2) \times 4) \times 6!) + F(F(F(6))))$
 22468 := $((2 - (-((2^4) \times 6!)) + F(F(8)))$
 22472 := $(2 \times ((2 + (F((F(4))!) \times F(7)))^2))$
 22478 := $(F(22) - (((F(4))! - F(F(7))) \times F(8)))$
 22483 := $((-(F(22)) - ((F(4))! \times F(8))) + (F(3))!)$
 22484 := $((-2) \times ((2^{F(4)!}) - F(F(8)))) + ((F(4))!)$
 22485 := $-(((F(22) + (4)) - 8!) + 5!)$
 22486 := $(((-2) + F((-2) + F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 8) - F(F(F(6)))$
 22496 := $(2 \times (((2 \times ((F(4))!)) - F(9)) \times F(6)))$
 22524 := $((F(((2+2)!)) + 5!)/2 - ((F(4))!))$
 22536 := $(-(((2+2)!)) \times ((-5!) \times F(3!)) + F(F(6)))$
 22537 := $(-(F(2) - (2^5))) \times ((3!)! + 7)$
 22538 := $((F(((2+2)!))/(5 - F(F(3)))) + F(F(8)))$
 22554 := $(-(F(22) + (55))) + (F((F(4))!))$
 22564 := $((-2) \times ((-((F(2) - (5))))! - F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4))!))$
 22568 := $-(((F(2) - (2^5)) \times (6! + 8)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22574 &:= (-((F(22) + (5 \times 7))) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 22583 &:= (-(((F(22) + (5)) + F(8))) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 22586 &:= ((2 \times (-F((2 + 5))) + F(F(8)))) + (6!) \\
 22588 &:= ((-F(22)) + (F((-((5 - 8))!))!) - (F(8))) \\
 22594 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) - 9)) + (((F(4))!))!) \\
 22596 &:= ((-(2 + 2)) + (5! \times 9)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 22597 &:= (((F(22) - 5!) - F(9)) + 7!) \\
 22599 &:= (((F(F((F((2 + 2))!)) \times 5!) - 9) \times 9) \\
 22603 &:= ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) - (03!) \\
 22604 &:= ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) - (0! + (4)) \\
 22605 &:= ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) + ((0! - (5))) \\
 22606 &:= ((-2) - F((F(2) + F(F(6)))))) - (0! - (F(6))!) \\
 22607 &:= ((-2) - F((F(2) + F(F(6)))))) + (((0! + (7))!)) \\
 22608 &:= -(((F(22) + ((6 \times 0))!) - 8!) \\
 22609 &:= (-F(22)) + (F((6 + (0 \times 9))))!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22610 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 0 \\
 22611 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 1 \\
 22612 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 2 \\
 22613 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 3 \\
 22614 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 4 \\
 22615 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 5 \\
 22616 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 6 \\
 22617 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 7 \\
 22618 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 8 \\
 22619 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + 1 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22624 &:= (((((F((2 + 2))! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 2) + ((F(4))!))!) \\
 22628 &:= ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) + (-2 + F(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22630 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 0 \\
 22631 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 1 \\
 22632 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 2 \\
 22633 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 3 \\
 22634 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 4 \\
 22635 &:= -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$22636 := -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 6$$

$$22637 := -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 7$$

$$22638 := -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 8$$

$$22639 := -F(22) + F(6)! + F(F(3!)) + 9$$

$$22643 := ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) + F((F(4))^{F(3)}))$$

$$22644 := (2 \times ((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(((F(4))! + F((F(4))!))))$$

$$22646 := (2 \times (F(F((2 + 6))) + F(((F(4))! + F(6))))$$

$$22648 := (2 \times ((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(((F(4))! + 8))))$$

$$22649 := (((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) + (F(4))!) + F(9)$$

$$22654 := (((F((F((2 + 2)))!))! / (-6)) \times (-5) - F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$22656 := (F((2 + 2)) \times (-((F(6)^5) + (F(6))!))$$

$$22659 := -((F(F((F((2 + 2)))!)) + (F(F(6)) \times (5! \times (-9))))$$

$$22664 := ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) + F((6 + 4))$$

$$22672 := -((F((F((2 + 2)))!)) + (((F(6))! + (7!)) / (-2)))$$

$$22673 := (-F(22)) - (-((F(6) + 7!) \times F(3!)))$$

$$22674 := -(((F((2 + 2)))! - ((F(6))! + (7!)) / F(F(4))))$$

$$22676 := (-((F(22) - 67)) + (F(6))!)$$

$$22679 := (-F(2)) - (((F(2) + F(6)))! / (-7 + 9))$$

$$22682 := (2 - (((F(2) + F(6)))! / (-8 \times 2)))$$

$$22687 := (F(22) + ((F(6) \times (-8)) + 7!))$$

$$22689 := ((F(2) + ((-((F(2) - (6))))! \times F(8))) \times 9)$$

$$22695 := ((-F(22)) + (F(6))!) - ((F(9) - 5!))$$

$$22697 := ((F(22) - ((6 \times 9))) + 7!)$$

$$22728 := (((F(22) + 7!) - 2) - F(8))$$

$$22730 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 0$$

$$22731 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 1$$

$$22732 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 2$$

$$22733 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 3$$

$$22734 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 4$$

$$22735 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 5$$

$$22736 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 6$$

$$22737 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 7$$

$$22738 := F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 8$$

- 22739 := $F(22) + 7! - F(F(3!)) + 9$
- 22742 := $((F(22) + 7!) - (F(4)^2))$
- 22743 := $((F(22) + 7!) - (4!/3))$
- 22744 := $((F(22) + 7!) - (4)) - F(4)$
- 22745 := $((F(22) + 7!) - F(F(F(4)))) - (5)$
- 22746 := $((F(22) + 7!) + F(4)) - F(6)$
- 22747 := $((F(22) - (7)) + F(4)) + 7!$
- 22748 := $((F(22) + 7!) - 4!) + F(8)$
- 22749 := $((F(22) + 7!) - F(-((F(4))! - 9)))$
- 22750 := $((F(22) + 7!) - ((5 \times 0)!)$
- 22751 := $(F(22) - (-7 \times ((5 + 1)!))$
- 22752 := $((F(22) + 7!) + F(F((5 - 2))))$
- 22753 := $((F(22) + 7!) + (5 - 3))$
- 22754 := $((F(22) + 7!) + (5)) - F(F(4))$
- 22759 := $((F(22) + 7!) + F((F(-((5 - 9))))!))$
- 22760 := $((F(22) + 7!) + F(6)) + 0!$
- 22763 := $((F(22) + 7!) + (6)) + 3!$
- 22764 := $((F(((2 + 2))!) - (7!/6)) / F(F(4)))$
- 22766 := $((F(22) + 7!) - (6)) + F(F(6))$
- 22772 := $((F(22) + 7!) + F((7 + F(2))))$
- 22777 := $((F(22) + F(7)) + F(7)) + 7!$
- 22778 := $-((F(22) - ((F(7) \times F(7)) + 8!)))$
- 22793 := $((F(22) + 7!) + F(9)) + F(3!)$
- 22824 := $((F(((2 + 2))!) - ((8 - 2)!)) / F(F(4)))$
- 22842 := $(-((F(22) - 8!)) + F(F(((F(4))! + F(2))))$
- 22847 := $((2 - (-2 \times F(F(8)))) + ((F(4))!)! + F(F(7)))$
- 22848 := $(-2 \times ((-((2 - 8))!) - ((4!)! / (F(8))!))$
- 22849 := $(F(2) - ((-28 \times 4!) \times F(9)))$
- 22852 := $((F(((2 + 2))!)! - ((F(F(8)) + 5!) \times (-2)))$
- 22853 := $((F(2) - (-2 \times F(F(8)))) - (-5! \times F(3!)))$
- 22854 := $(2 \times ((F(2) + F(F(8))) - (5! \times (-4))))$
- 22856 := $((2 \times (2 + F(F(8)))) + (5! \times F(6)))$
- 22866 := $(-2 \times (F(F(-((F(2) - 8)))) + (-6! - F(F(F(6)))))$
- 22867 := $(F(2) + (2 \times ((F(F(8)) + (6!) - F(F(7))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22874 &:= (2 + (((-(2 - 8)))! + F(F(7))) \times 4!) \\
 22894 &:= ((F((F((2 + 2))))!)! + (-F(F(8))) - (9 \times ((F(4))!))) \\
 22896 &:= (2 \times ((-2) + F(F(8))) + ((9!/6!))) \\
 22914 &:= (2 \times (((2^9) - 1) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 22932 &:= ((F(((2 + 2)!)) + (-9!)/(3!))/2) \\
 22943 &:= (-F(2)) + ((-2) + F(9)) \times (-F(4) + 3!!) \\
 22944 &:= (((F(2) \times (-2)) + F(9)) \times (((F(4))! - F(4))) \\
 22946 &:= (2 - ((-2) + F(9)) \times (F(4) - 6!)) \\
 22964 &:= (2 \times (((2^9) + F(F(F(6)))) + (4!))) \\
 23034 &:= (((2 + 30) \times (3!)! - (F(4))!) \\
 23036 &:= ((F(2) + 3) \times (-0!) - (F(3!) \times (-6!))) \\
 23039 &:= (-F(2)) + ((3!)! \times ((0 - F(3)) + F(9))) \\
 \\
 23040 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 0 \\
 23041 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 1 \\
 23042 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 2 \\
 23043 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 3 \\
 23044 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 4 \\
 23045 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 5 \\
 23046 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 6 \\
 23047 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 7 \\
 23048 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 8 \\
 23049 &:= (2 + 30) \times F(4)!! + 9 \\
 \\
 23056 &:= (((-2) \times (3!)! - 0!) \times (5 - F(F(6)))) \\
 23057 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((0 - 5) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 23065 &:= (-2) + (F(F((3! + 0!))) \times (-F(F(6)) - 5!)) \\
 23067 &:= (((2 + 3)! - F(F(06))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 23076 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (0! - F(F(7)))) + (6!)) \\
 23088 &:= (-2) + (((((3 + 0!)!)/(F(8))!) + F(F(8))) \\
 23104 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(3!)) + (F(10))))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 23136 &:= ((F(2) + (31)) \times (3 + 6!)) \\
 23142 &:= ((-2) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(((1 \times 4)!)/2)) \\
 23143 &:= ((-2) \times F(F(3!))) + (1 - (F(4!)/(-F(3)))) \\
 23144 &:= (-2) \times (F(F(3!)) - (1 - (F(4!)/(-4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 23147** := $((-2) + F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) + (4^7)$
23149 := $(((-2) + F(((3 + 1)!)))/F(F(4))) - F(9)$
23152 := $((-(2^{3!})) + F((-((1 - 5)))!))/2$
23154 := $((2 \times F(((3 + 1)!)) - 5!)/4$
23185 := $((2 + F(((3 + 1)!)))/F((8 - 5)))$
23186 := $(2 - (F(((3 + 1)!)/(-8 - 6)))$
23204 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) - 0!) + F(F((F(4)!)))$
23205 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + F(F((0! + (5))))$
23206 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + (0! + F(F(6))))$
23218 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + F((1 + 8)))$
23219 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + (1 + F(9)))$
23226 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + (2 \times F(F(6))))$
23233 := $(F(2) - (32 \times (-3!) - 3!))$
23234 := $(2 + (32 \times ((3!)! + (F(4)!)))$
23236 := $(2 \times ((32 \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(6))))$
23238 := $((F(2) + F(3!)) \times (-2) + F((-3) + F(8)))$
23239 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + F((F(F(3)) + 9)))$
23242 := $(-2) - ((-((3 + 2)! - F(4!))/2)$
23243 := $(((-2) + ((3 + 2)! + F(4!))/F(3)$
23244 := $((((2 + 3)! + F(24))/F(F(4)))$
23245 := $(-2) + (F(F(3!)) \times (F((2^4) + 5!))$
23248 := $(2 \times ((F(F(3!)) \times (-2)) + ((F(4)!!) + F(F(8))))$
23256 := $((F(2) + F(3!)) \times F(-((2 - 5) \times 6)))$
23264 := $(2 \times ((-F((3^2))) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4)!!)!)$
23265 := $((2 + F(F((3! + F(2)))) \times (-F(F(6) - 5!))$
23268 := $(2 \times ((-32) + 6!) + F(F(8)))$
23273 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) + F((F(7) - F(3))))$
23278 := $(2 \times (((3!)! - 27) + F(F(8))))$
23284 := $(2 \times (((3!)! + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - (4!))$
23286 := $(2 \times (((3!)! - 2) + F(F(8)) - F(F(6))))$
23288 := $(2 \times (((3!)! - (F(2) + F(8))) + F(F(8))))$
23295 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/2) - (9 - 5!))$
23296 := $((2^{F(3!)} - ((2 - F(9)) \times 6!))$
23304 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/F(3)) + (((0! + (4)!))!))$
23305 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)!)/F(3)) + ((0! + 5!))$

$$\begin{aligned}23306 &:= (2 \times (((3!)! - F((3! + 0!))) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\23312 &:= (((2^{F(3!)}) + F(((3 + 1)!)))/2) \\23313 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (((3!)! + 1)))) - (F(F(3!)))) \\23314 &:= (2 \times ((F(3!))! + (-3!) - F((-1 + 4!)))) \\23316 &:= (2 \times (((3!)! - F(3!)) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))))) \\23317 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (((3!)! - 1)))) - F(7)) \\23318 &:= (2 \times (((3!)! - (3! + 1)) + F(F(8)))) \\23320 &:= (2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + ((3!)! - ((2 + 0!)!))) \\23322 &:= (((-F(23)) + (F(3!)!)) - 2) \times 2) \\23323 &:= (F(2) - (((3^{3!})/(-2)) + 3!)) \\23326 &:= (((F(F(2^3)) + 3!!) \times 2) - 6) \\23327 &:= -((F(2) + (-3) \times (3!^{-2+7}))) \\23329 &:= (F(2) - ((3^{3!}) \times (2 - F(9))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23330 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 0 \\23331 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 1 \\23332 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 2 \\23333 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 3 \\23334 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 4 \\23335 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 5 \\23336 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 6 \\23337 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 7 \\23338 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 8 \\23339 &:= 2 + 3!^{3!}/F(3) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23340 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 0 \\23341 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 1 \\23342 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 2 \\23343 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 3 \\23344 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 4 \\23345 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 5 \\23346 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 6 \\23347 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 7 \\23348 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 8 \\23349 &:= 2 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 3!! + 4) + 9\end{aligned}$$

- 23350** := $(2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (3^{5+0!})))$
23352 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)))! - ((F((3)!))! / (-5!))) / 2)$
23353 := $(F(2) - ((F((3)!) + (((3)!)^5)) \times (-3))$
23356 := $(2 \times (((3)! \times (F(3) + (5)!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
23358 := $(2 \times (((3)!)! + F((F(3) + (5)))) + F(F(8)))$
23362 := $(F((F(2) + F((3)!))) - (((3)!)^6) / (-2))$
23364 := $((((2 \times 3)!) - (3^{F(6)})) \times (-4))$
23366 := $(2 \times (((3^3!) + F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))$
23367 := $((2 \times (((3)!)! + F(F((3)!))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 7)$
23368 := $(2 \times (((3 \times 3)!) + (6)!) + F(F(8)))$
23374 := $(-2) + (F(3) \times (((3)!)! - F(F(7))) \times (4)!))$
23376 := $((2 \times 3) \times (((3)!)! - F(F(7))) \times F(6))$
23377 := $((2 \times (F(-F(F(3))) + F(F((3)!))) + ((7)!)) - F(F(7)))$
23378 := $(2 + (3)! \times (((3)!)! - F(F(7))) \times 8))$
23379 := $((2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (((3)!)!)) + (F(7) + F(9)))$
23384 := $(2 \times (((F(3) + ((3)!)!) + F(F(8))) + ((4)!))$
23386 := $(2 \times ((3^3) + F(F(8))) + ((6)!))$
23387 := $((2 \times (F(F((3)!)) + (((3)!)! + F(F(8)))) + F(7))$
23392 := $((2 + (3^3!)) \times (F(9) - 2))$
23394 := $(((-F(23)) + (F((3)!)!) + F(9)) \times F(F(4)))$
23395 := $((2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (((3)!)! + F(9)))) - (5))$
23396 := $(2 \times (((3)!)! - ((F(3) - F(9)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
23398 := $(2 \times (((3)!)! - F(F(3))) + F(9)) + F(F(8)))$
23414 := $(2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (41 + ((F(4)!)!)))$
23417 := $((F(((F(2) + 3)))! / F(F(4))) - (-1 \times F(F(7))))$
23423 := $(F(F((F(2) + (3)!))) - ((F((4)!)/(-2)) - (3)!))$
23425 := $((((-2) - ((3)!)!) - F((4)!)) / (-2) - (5)!)$
23427 := $((2 + F((3)!)) - ((F((4)!)/(-2)) - F(F(7))))$
23428 := $(2 \times (((3)!)! + ((4)! \times 2)) + F(F(8)))$
23432 := $(-(2^{F(3!)})) - (-((4)! \times F((F(3)! \times 2))))$
23434 := $((2^{F(3!)} - ((F((4)!)/(-F(3))) + (F(4)!))$
23435 := $((2^{F(3!)} - ((F((4)!)/(-F(3))) + (5)))$
23437 := $((-F(2) + F(F((3)!))) - ((F((4)!)/(-F(3))) - F(F(7))))$
23438 := $(F(F((F(2) + (3)!))) - ((F((4)!)/(-F(3))) - (F(8))))$

$$23440 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 0$$

$$23441 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 1$$

$$23442 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 2$$

$$23443 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 3$$

$$23444 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 4$$

$$23445 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 5$$

$$23446 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 6$$

$$23447 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 7$$

$$23448 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 8$$

$$23449 := 2^{F(3!)} + F(4!)/F(F(4)) + 9$$

$$23451 := ((2 \times (F(F(F((3)!)))) + (((F(4))!)!)) + (((5)! - 1)))$$

$$23452 := (2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (((F(4))!)! + ((5)!/2)))$$

$$23453 := ((2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (((F(4))!)!)) + ((5)! + F(F(3))))$$

$$23454 := (((2 \times F(F((3)!))) + ((F(4))!^5)) \times F(4))$$

$$23459 := (-F(2) + (((3)! - ((F(4))! \times 5)) \times F(9)))$$

$$23463 := (((-F(2) + ((3)!!) \times F((F(4))!)) + F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))))))$$

$$23465 := (((2 + ((3)!!)/F(F(4))) \times 65)$$

$$23467 := ((-F(2) + (F((3)!))!) + ((-F(F(4))) \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((7)!))$$

$$23468 := (((((F(2) + F((3)!))!)/F((F(4))!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(8)))$$

$$23469 := -((F((2 \times F((3)!))) + ((4)! - ((6)! \times F(9))))$$

$$23470 := (F((F(2) + F(F((3)!)))) + (((F(4))!)! + ((7)! - 0!)))$$

$$23471 := (F((F(2) + F(F((3)!)))) + (((F(4))!)! \times (7 + 1)))$$

$$23472 := (((2^3)! - (F((4)!)/(-7)))/2)$$

$$23473 := ((-2) \times (((3)!! + F((4)!)) + ((7^3)))$$

$$23474 := (2 + (((F((3)!))! - (F((4)!)/(-7)))/F(F(4))))$$

$$23475 := -((F((-F(2) + F(F((3)!)))) + (((F(4) + (7))!)/(-5)!)))$$

$$23476 := ((F((2 \times F((3)!))) \times (4)! - (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))))$$

$$23478 := (2 \times (((F((3)!))!)/F(4)! + ((7)! - F(8))))$$

$$23479 := (((F(2) + ((3)!!) \times F((F(4))!)) + (F((F(7) + 9))))$$

$$23483 := ((2 \times F(F(F((3)!))) + (F((-4) + F(8))) - (3)!))$$

$$23486 := (F((F(2) + F(F((3)!)))) + ((F((4)!)/8) - F(F(6))))$$

$$23488 := ((-F(2) + F(F(F((3)!)))) + (F((-4) + F(8))) + F(F(8))))$$

$$23489 := ((2 \times F((-3) + (4)!)) + (F((8 + 9))))$$

- 23490 := (((2 × F(F(F((3)!)))) + F((F((F(4))!) + 9))) + 0!)
 23492 := -((F((2 × F((3)!))) + (((F(4))!)! × (-F(9))) + F(2)))
 23493 := ((-F(2)) × F((F(3)⁴))) - (-F(9) × ((3)!))
 23494 := (-2) + (((3)!! - F((F(4))!)) × (9 + (4)!))
 23496 := -((F((2 × F((3)!))) - ((F(4) + (F(9) × (6)!))))
 23497 := ((F(23) - (-((4 - 9)))!) - ((7)!))
 23498 := ((F((-2) + F(F((3)!))) × F(4) + (9 + F(F(8))))
 23513 := (-((F(2) + (3)!)⁵) + (F(((1 × 3)!))!))
 23514 := (-(((F(2) + (3)!)⁵ - 1)) + (F((F(4))!))!))
 23529 := (((-2) + ((3)!!) - (5)) × (-F(2) - F(9)))
 23533 := (F(F((F(2) + (3)!))) × (((5)! - F(F((3)!))) + F(3)))
 23534 := ((-((F(2) + (3)!)⁵) + (F((3)!))!) + F(F((F(4))!)))
 23542 := (((F(2) + ((3)!!) - (5)) + F((4)!)) / 2)
 23543 := (((-2) + ((3)! × (5)!)) + F((4)!)) / F(3)
 23544 := ((F((2 × (3 + 5))) - (F(4))!) × (4)!))
 23545 := ((-F(2) + F(F(F((3)!)))) + ((-((5)! × F(F((F(4))!))) × (-5)))
 23546 := (2 + (3 × ((5)! + (F((4)! / 6))))
 23548 := (2 + ((F(F((3)!)) × (-((5)! + ((F(4))!)!)) + F(F(8))))
 23556 := (((2 - (F(F((3)!)) × (-5)!)) × 5) + F(F(F(6))))
 23562 := ((2 × F(F((3)!)) × ((5)! + (F(F(6))²)))
 23564 := (2 × (((((3)!!) + (5)! + F(F(F(6)))) - 4))
 23566 := (2 × (((-3) + (5)! + (6)! + F(F(F(6))))))
 23568 := (2 × (-(((F(3) - (5)! - (6)!)) + F(F(8))))
 23570 := (2 × (F(F(F((3)!))) + (((5)! × 7) - 0!)))
 23571 := ((2 × (F(F(F((3)!))) + ((5)! × 7)) - 1)
 23572 := ((F(F(2³)) + ((5)! × 7)) × 2)
 23573 := (F(2) + ((F(F(F((3)!))) + ((5)! × 7)) × F(3)))
 23574 := (((-F(2) - F(F(F((3)!)))) - ((5)! × 7)) × (-F(F(4))))
 23576 := (((2 + ((3)!!) + (5)! × (7 + F(F(6))))
 23578 := (2 × ((3 + ((5)! × 7)) + F(F(8))))
 23584 := (2 × (((((3)!!) + (5)! + F(F(8))) + (F(4))!))
 23588 := (((2 + ((3)!!) - (5)! × F(8)) + F(F(8)))
 23593 := (-2) + (((3)!! - (5)) × (F(9) - F(F(3))))
 23594 := (((2^{F(3)}) - (5)) × 94)
 23596 := ((F((-2) + F(F((3)!))) × (5 - 9)) + (F(6))!))

$$\begin{aligned} 23614 &:= ((F(23) - ((6 + 1)!) - F(4)) \\ 23616 &:= ((-F(2)) + F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) - ((1 + 6)!) \\ 23617 &:= (F(23) - ((6 + (1^7)))!) \\ 23618 &:= ((F(2) + F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) - (-((1 - 8)))!) \\ 23623 &:= ((F(23) + (6)) - ((F(2) + (3)!)!) \\ 23624 &:= ((F(F(2^3)) - ((F(6) - F(2))!) \times 4) \\ 23625 &:= ((F(23) + F(6)) - ((2 + 5)!) \\ 23627 &:= (((F(23) + F(6)) + 2) - (7)!) \\ 23632 &:= (((((2 + F(F(F((3)!)))) \times F(6)) - (F((3)!)!)/2) \\ 23633 &:= (F((F(2) + F(F((3)!)))) + (F((F(6) \times F(3))) \times (3)!) \\ 23634 &:= (((F(2) + ((3)!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (3)!) - F((4)!) \\ 23636 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (F(6)^3))) + ((6)!) \\ 23637 &:= (((F(23) + F(F(6))) - F(F(3))) - (7)!) \\ 23638 &:= (F(23) - (((F(6)!/F((3)!) - (F(8)))) \\ \\ 23640 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 0 \\ 23641 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 1 \\ 23642 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 2 \\ 23643 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 3 \\ 23644 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 4 \\ 23645 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 5 \\ 23646 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 6 \\ 23647 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 7 \\ 23648 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 8 \\ 23649 &:= (-2 + F(F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4! + 9 \\ \\ 23654 &:= -((F((F(2) + F((3)!))) + (F((F(F(6)) - (5))) \times (-4)!) \\ 23657 &:= (F(23) - ((F(6) \times (-5)) + (7)!) \\ 23666 &:= ((((-2) \times (F((3)!)!)/(-6)) - ((6)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 23668 &:= (2 \times (((F((3)!) \times F(F(6))) + ((6)!) + F(F(8)))) \\ 23673 &:= (((F(2) - F(F((3)!))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7)))/(-3)!) \\ 23679 &:= -((F((-F(2)) + F(F((3)!))) + (-6) \times ((7)! + F(9))) \\ 23684 &:= (((F(2) + 3)! \times F((F(6) + 8))) - 4) \\ 23692 &:= (-2) - ((F(3) - (6)!) \times (F(9) - F(2))) \\ 23693 &:= ((F(2) - ((F(3) - (6)!) \times F(9))) - ((3)!) \end{aligned}$$

- 23694** := (((-23) + (6)!) × F(9)) - (4)
23696 := -(((2^{3!}) - (((6)! × F(9)) - (6)!)))
23697 := (F(23) - (((6)! / (-9)) + (7)!))
23698 := ((-23) + (6)!) × F(((9)! / (8)!))
23706 := ((F((2 + F((3)!))) × (F(F(7)) - 0!)) + F(F(F(6))))
23712 := (((-2) + F(F(F((3)!)))) × (-F(7))) / (-((1 + 2)!))
23714 := (2 - ((F(3 + F(7))) + 1) × (-4)!))
23716 := ((-2) - (F(F(F((3)!))) × (-F(7)))) / (1 × 6)
23718 := (-2) × (F(F((3)!)) + (((F(7) - 1)! / (-8)!)))
23724 := (((F(2) + F(F((3)!))) × 7²) + F((F(4)!))
23726 := (((F(2) - ((3)!)) × (-F((7 + 2)))) - ((6)!))
23727 := ((F(2) - ((3)!)) × ((F(7) × (-2)) - (7)))
23733 := ((((-2) + F(F(F((3)!)))) × (-F(7))) / (-3!)) + (F(F((3)!)))
23734 := (-2) + ((F(3) + F((F(7) + 3))) × (4)!))
23735 := (((F(23) - (7)!) - F(3)) + (5)!)
23737 := ((F(23) + ((7 - F(3)))!) - ((7)!))
23738 := ((F((2 × F((3)!))) + ((7)!)) + F((F(F(3)) + (F(8))))
23743 := (F(23) - ((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4)))) × F(F((3)!)))
23744 := (F(23) - ((-7) + (4)!)^{F(4)})
23745 := ((-2) × ((3)!)) + (((7)! - F(4)) × 5)
23746 := (F((F(2) + F(F((3)!)))) + ((-F(7)) + F((4)!)) - (F(6)!))
23747 := (((2 × (3)!))! / ((7)! × 4)) - F(7)
23749 := ((-F(2)) - (-((3)! × F(F(7)))) × (F((F(4)!)) + 9))
23754 := (((-2) × ((3)!)) - ((7)! × (-5))) - (F(4)!)
23756 := (2 × (-F(3)) - (-((7 + 5)! / (F(6)!)))
23758 := (((F(23) - (7)!) + (5)!) + F(8))
23759 := -((F(2) - ((3)! × ((7)! - ((5)! × 9))))

23760 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 0
23761 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 1
23762 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 2
23763 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 3
23764 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 4
23765 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 5
23766 := (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) × 6! + 6

$$\begin{aligned}
 23767 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 7 \\
 23768 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 8 \\
 23769 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(3) + 7)) \times 6! + 9 \\
 \\
 23774 &:= (((-2) + (F((3)!) \times F(7))) \times F(F(7))) + F((F(4))!) \\
 23776 &:= (2 \times (F((3)!) + (((F(7))!/F(7))/F(6)!)) \\
 23777 &:= ((F((2 \times F((3)!))) \times F(7)) + F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) \\
 23778 &:= (2 \times ((-(3^7) \times F(7)) + (8)!)) \\
 23779 &:= ((2 + F(F(F((3)!)))) + ((F(7) \times F((7 + 9)))) \\
 23783 &:= ((F((2 \times F((3)!))) \times F(7)) + ((F(F(8)) + (3)!)) \\
 23784 &:= (((-2) + ((3)!!) + (F(7) \times F(8))) \times (4)!) \\
 23785 &:= ((-2) + ((3)!!) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(8) - (5)!)) \\
 23786 &:= (2 \times (((-(3)!) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) + ((6)!)) \\
 23789 &:= ((2 \times (((3)!! + F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))) - 9) \\
 23793 &:= ((-F(2)) - ((3)!!) \times ((7 - F(9)) - (3)!) \\
 23794 &:= (((F(2) + (3 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(9)) - (F(4))!) \\
 23796 &:= ((((-F(2)) + ((3)!!) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(9))) + (F(6))!) \\
 23812 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F((3)!)))) + ((8)!/F(F(((1 + 2)!)))) \\
 23824 &:= (((F((2 \times (3)!)) + 8)^2) + ((F(4))!)) \\
 23826 &:= (((2 \times (3)!) + F(8)) \times (2 + (6)!)) \\
 23833 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F((3)!)))) + (((8)!/F(F((3)!))) + F(F((3)!))) \\
 23834 &:= (((2 + ((3)!!) - (F(8))) \times 34) \\
 23844 &:= (2 \times (((3)!! + F(F(8))) + (4^4)) \\
 23854 &:= (2 \times ((F(F((3)!)) + F(F(8))) + ((5)! \times F((F(4))!))) \\
 23858 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (F((F(8) - (5)))))) - 8) \\
 23865 &:= ((F((2 \times F((3)!))) - (8 \times (6)!)) \times (-5)) \\
 23869 &:= (F(2) - (((-3) + F(8)) - (6)!) \times F(9)) \\
 23878 &:= (2 \times (((3)!! + F(F(8))) + (F(7) \times F(8))) \\
 23879 &:= (((-F(2)) + ((3)!!) + (8)!) + ((F(7))!/(-9)!) \\
 23882 &:= (2 \times ((F((3)!) + F(F(8))) + (F((8 \times 2)))) \\
 23898 &:= (((-23) \times F(8)) \times F(9)) + (8)!) \\
 23904 &:= ((F((2 \times F((3)!))) + 9) \times (04)!) \\
 23906 &:= (((2 \times ((3)!!) \times 9) + F(F(F(06)))) \\
 23908 &:= ((2 \times (((3)!! \times 9) + 0!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 23924 &:= (((-F(2)) - ((3)!!) \times (-9 \times 2)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 23927 := (((2 - ((3)!)!) × (-F(9) - F(2))) + F(F(7)))
- 23934 := (((F(2) - ((3)!)!) × (-F(9))) - (F((3)!)^{F(4)}))
- 23936 := (((2^{3!}) × F(9)) × (3 + F(6)))
- 23938 := (((2 + ((3)!)!) × F((9 + F(3)))) - (8)!))
- 23943 := ((-F(2) - ((F(F((3)!)!)!)/(9 × F(F(4))))!) × (-3))
- 23947 := ((2 + (F((3)!)!)) + (9 - (4⁷)))
- 23948 := ((2 × (F(F((3)!)!)) + (9 × ((F(4)!)!))) + F(F(8)))
- 23953 := (F(2) + (((3)!)! + ((9)!/(-5)))/(-3))
- 23954 := (2 + (((3)!)! + ((9)!/(-5)))/(-F(4)))
- 23956 := (F(2) + (F((F((3)!) + 9)) × ((5)!/F(6))))
- 23957 := (-2 + ((F((3)!) × ((9)!/5!)) - F(F(7))))
- 23958 := ((F(F((F(2) + (3)!)!)) + 9) × ((5)! - F(8)))
- 23963 := ((-F(2) - ((3)!)! + ((F(9) × ((6)! + (3)!)!)))
- 23964 := (-(((2 × 3)!) + (F(9) × ((6)! + (F(4)!)!)))
- 23966 := ((2 - ((3)!)!) + (F(9) × ((6)! + (6))))
- 23969 := ((F(2) - (F(3)⁹)) + ((6)! × F(9)))
- 23974 := (-((2^{3!})) - (F(9) × (F(7) - ((F(4)!)!)))
- 23975 := (((-F(2) + ((3)!)!) - F(9)) × (7 × 5))
- 23984 := ((2 × (((3)!)! - F(9)) + F(F(8))) + ((F(4)!)!))
- 23989 := ((2 × F(F(F((3)!)!))) - (F((F(9) - F(8))) × (-9)))
- 23991 := (((-2) + ((3)!)!) + 9) × (F(9) - 1)
- 23994 := (((2 + F((F(3) × 9))) × 9) + ((F(4)!)!))
- 24024 := (((2 × ((F(4)!)! + 0!))!)/(2 + F((F(4)!)!))!)
- 24035 := (((F(2) + (F(4)!)!)! - F(F((0! + (3)!)!))) × 5)
- 24037 := (((2 × F(F((F(4)!)!))) + 0!)^{F(3)}) × F(7)
- 24039 := (F(2) - (((F(4)!)! - F((0! + (3)!)!)) × (-F(9))))
- 24043 := ((-2) + F((F(F((F(4)!)!)) - 0!)) + ((4)! × ((3)!)!))
- 24044 := (F((-F(2) + F(F((F(4)!)!)))) + (-0! - (-((4)! × ((F(4)!)!))))
- 24046 := ((2 × ((F((F(4)!)!)! - (F(-((0! - (4)!)!)))))) + ((6)!))
- 24048 := (-2) × (((4 + 0!)! - (((4)!)!/(F(8)!)!))
- 24064 := (((2 × (4)!) - 0!) × (F(6)^{F(4)}))
- 24079 := ((F(2) + ((4 + 0!)!) × (F(F(7)) - F(9)))
- 24128 := ((2^{F(4)!}) × F((((1 + 2)!) + 8))
- 24144 := ((2 - (F((F(4)!)! × (-F(14)))) × F((F(4)!)!))

$$\begin{aligned} 24176 &:= ((-2) + (F(F((F(4)!))) \times F((-1 + F(7)))))) \times F(6)) \\ 24178 &:= ((2^{F(F(4)!+1)}) + ((7)! + F(F(8)))) \\ 24184 &:= (((-2) + F((4)!)) - ((1 \times 8)!)) \times 4 \\ 24192 &:= (2 \times ((F((4)! - ((1 - 9)))!)) \times 2) \\ 24193 &:= (F(2) - (((F((F(4)! + 1))!)/(-9 - (3)!))) \\ 24194 &:= (2 + ((F((4)! - ((1 - 9)))!)) \times 4) \\ 24196 &:= (2 \times (((F((F(4)!))!)/(1 + F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\ 24208 &:= (F((F(2) + F((F(4)!))) \times (((2 + 0!)! - 8)) \\ 24209 &:= (F(2) + (((F(4)! - F((2 + 0!)!)) \times F(9))) \\ 24213 &:= (((2 \times ((4)!^2) + 1) \times F(F((3)!))) \\ 24227 &:= ((F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!)))) - (((F((2 + 2)))!)) \times 7) \\ 24234 &:= (((F(2) + ((4)!^2) \times F(F((3)!))) \times F(F(4))) \\ 24235 &:= ((-F(2) + F((4)!)) + (-2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + (5)!))) \\ 24244 &:= ((2 \times (((4)! - ((-2) + (4)!))!)) / (F(F((F(4)!))!)) \\ 24246 &:= (2 \times (((4)! / (F((2 \times 4)))! - F(F(6)))) \\ 24247 &:= ((F((F(2) + (4 \times 2))) \times ((F(4)! - F(F(7)))) \\ 24248 &:= (((F((2 + F((F(4)!)))^2) + (F(4)! \times 8) \\ 24249 &:= ((2 - F(F(((F(4)! + F(2)))))) - (((F(4)! - F(9)))) \\ 24253 &:= (-2) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (F((2 \times 5)) \times F(F((3)!)))) \\ 24254 &:= (-F(2) + ((F(F((F(4)!))^2) \times F((5 \times F(F(4)))))) \\ 24256 &:= (F(2) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-F((2 \times 5)) \times F(F(6)))))) \\ 24258 &:= (((2 + F(((4)! + 2)))/5) - F(8)) \\ 24264 &:= ((24 + F((2 \times F(6)))) \times (4)!) \\ 24266 &:= (((2 \times ((4)! - (F(2) + F(F(6))))!)) / (F(F(6))!)) \\ 24268 &:= (F(2) + (((((4)! \times 2) / (F(F(6))!)) - F(8))) \\ 24274 &:= (-2) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (F((2 + 7))^{F(F(4))})) \\ 24275 &:= (-F(2) - ((F(((4)! + 2) - F(7)) / (-5))) \\ 24279 &:= (((2 \times ((4)! - (F((F(2) + 7))))!)) - 9) \\ 24283 &:= (F(2) + (((((4)! \times 2) / (F(8)!)) - (3)!)) \\ 24284 &:= (((2 \times ((4)! - (F(2) \times F(8))))!)) - 4) \\ 24285 &:= (2 - (((((4)! \times (-2)) / (F(8)!)) + (5))) \\ 24286 &:= ((2 \times ((4)! - (F(2) \times F(8))))! / (F(F(6))!)) \\ 24287 &:= (-F(2) + (((((4)! \times 2) / ((8 + F(7))))!)) \\ 24288 &:= ((2 \times ((4)! - (F((2 \times 8) - 8)))!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24290 &:= (2 - (((4)!)! \times (-2)) / (F((9 - 0!)!))) \\
 24292 &:= (2 \times (((4)!)! / (F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + 2) \\
 24294 &:= (((2 \times ((4)!)! / (F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + (F(4)!) \\
 24296 &:= (((2 \times ((4)!)! / (F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + F(6)) \\
 24299 &:= (2 + (F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times (F(2) + (F(9) \times F(9)))) \\
 24304 &:= (2 \times (((4)!)! / (F(F((3)!)!)) + F((F(04)!)!)) \\
 24306 &:= (2 \times (((4)!)! / (F(F((3)!)!)) + (0! + F(6))) \\
 24308 &:= (((2 \times ((4)!)! / (F(F((3)!)!)) - ((0! - F(8)))) \\
 24309 &:= (-F(2)) + (((-4) + ((3)!)! - 0!) \times F(9)) \\
 24310 &:= ((F(2) + (F(F((F(4)!)!)^{F(3)})) \times F(10)) \\
 24312 &:= (2 \times (((4)!)! / (F(F((3)!)!)) + 12) \\
 24314 &:= (2 \times (((4)!)! / (F(F((3)!)!)) + F((1 + (F(4)!)!))) \\
 24326 &:= (((-(F(2) - (4)!)^3) \times 2) - F(6)) \\
 24327 &:= (((-(F(2) - (4)!)^3) \times 2) - 7) \\
 \\
 24330 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 0 \\
 24331 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 1 \\
 24332 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 2 \\
 24333 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 3 \\
 24334 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 4 \\
 24335 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 5 \\
 24336 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 6 \\
 24337 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 7 \\
 24338 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 8 \\
 24339 &:= 2 \times (4!! / F(F(3)!)! + F(F(3))) + 9 \\
 \\
 24340 &:= (F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!)!))) + (((F((3)!)! / F(F(4))) - 0!)) \\
 24341 &:= (F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!)!))) + ((F((3)!)! / F((4 - 1)))) \\
 24342 &:= (((-(F(2) - (4)!)^3) + 4) \times 2) \\
 24343 &:= (-F(2)) + (((-4) + ((3)!)! \times F((F(4)^{F(3)}))) \\
 24344 &:= (((F(2) \times (-4)) + ((3)!)! \times F((F(4) \times F(4)))) \\
 24345 &:= (F(2) + ((4 - ((3)!)!) \times (-F((4 + 5)))) \\
 24346 &:= (2 \times (((4)! - F(F(3)))^{F(4)} + 6)) \\
 24347 &:= (((-(F(2) - (4)!)^3) \times F(F(4))) + F(7)) \\
 24348 &:= (((2 - (4)!) \times (((3)!)! + (F(4)!)!)) + (8)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 24349** := $((F(2) + (4)) - (((3)!)! - 4) \times (-F(9)))$
24350 := $((F(F((F(2) + (F(4)!)))) - ((3)!)!) \times (-50))$
24354 := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4)!)))) \times ((3)!)! - ((5)! + (F(4)!)!))$
24355 := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4)!)))) \times ((3)!)! + (-5) - (5)!)!$
24356 := $((2 \times F(((4)! - F(3)))) - (5)! - F(F(F(6))))$
24357 := $((F(2) - (4)!) \times (-3)) \times ((5)! + F(F(7)))$
24358 := $((2 + F((4)!) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + (-((5)! - F(F(8))))$
24360 := $-(((F(2) + (4)))! - (((3)!)! \times F((F(6) + 0!))))$
24362 := $(F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!)))) + (F(F((3)!) + ((F(6)!)! / 2)))$
24363 := $((-2) - (4)!) + ((F((3)!) + F(F(6)))^3)$
24364 := $(-((F(2) + (4)!) + ((F((3)!) + F(F(6)))^{F(4)}))$
24365 := $(-F(2) + ((F(4)!) \times (F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - (5)!))$
24366 := $((F(((2^4) + 3)) \times 6) - (6)!)!$
24367 := $((F(2) - ((F(4)!)!) + ((3)! \times F((6 + F(7))))$
24368 := $((F((2 + F((F(4)!)!))^{F(3)} + (F(F(6)))) \times 8)$
24369 := $((-F(2) - F((F(4)!)!)) - ((3 - (6)!) \times F(9)))$
24373 := $(((((2 \times 4)!) / 3) - F(7)) + F(F(F((3)!))))$
24374 := $((F(2) + (((F((F(4)!)!)! / 3) - F(7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))$
24375 := $((-2) + F(((F(4)!) + F((3)!)))) \times (F(7) \times 5)$
24376 := $(-2) + ((-F(4) + ((3)!)!) \times (F(7) + F(F(6))))$
24377 := $((F(2) - F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) + (((3)! + (7)!) \times 7))$
24378 := $((((2 + 4)!) - 3) \times (F(7) + F(8)))$
24379 := $(F(2) + (((4 + ((3)!)!) - 7) \times F(9)))$
24380 := $(2 - ((F(4) - ((3)!)!) \times F((8 + 0!)))$
24382 := $(F(2) + (F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times (((3)!)! + (F(8)^2))))$
24383 := $(F(F((2 \times 4))) - (3 - ((8)! / 3))$
24385 := $(-F(2) - (((F((F(4)!)!)! / (-3)) - F(F(F(((8 - 5)!)!))))$
24386 := $(F(F((2 \times 4))) + ((F(3) \times (8)!) / 6))$
24387 := $(-2) + ((F((F(4)!) + F(F((3)!)))^{F(8)/7})$
24390 := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4)!)))) \times ((3)!)! - (90))$
24393 := $((2 - F((F(4) + F((3)!)))) - (-F(9) \times ((3)!)!))$
24394 := $(-((2 \times 43)) - (-F(9) \times ((F(4)!)!))$
24395 := $(-F(2) + (((F(4)!) - ((3)!)!) \times (-F(9))) + (5)!)!$
24396 := $((F(2) \times (-4)) \times F(F((3)!)) + ((F(9) \times (6)!)!))$

- 24397 := $(-2) + (((F(F(4)) - ((3)!)!) \times (-F(9))) - F(7))$
 24398 := $(-F(2)) + (((-F(4) + ((3)!)!) \times F(9)) + (F(8)))$
 24399 := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4))!))) \times ((3)!)!) - ((9 \times 9)))$
 24404 := $(((-2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F((F((F(4))!) + 0!))) - F((F(4))!))$
 24406 := $(((-2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F((F((F(4))!) + 0!))) - 6$
 24411 := $(((-2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F((F((F(4))!) + 1))) - 1$
 24412 := $((-2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F(((4 - 1)^2))$
 24413 := $(F(2) + (((F(4))! - F(F(4))) \times F((1 + F((3)!))))$
 24414 := $(((-2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F((F((F(4))!) + 1))) + F(F(4))$
 24416 := $(-(2^{F(4)!})) - (((F(4))! \times (-F((1 + F(6))))))$
 24423 := $((2 + ((F(4))!)) + (F(F((F(4))!)^2)) \times F(F((3)!))$
 24424 := $((((2 + (4)!) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-2)) + F((4)!))$
 24425 := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4))!))) \times ((F(4))!)) - F((2 \times 5)))$
 24428 := $((F((-2) + (4)!)) - ((4)!) \times 2) - F(F(8))$
 24430 := $(-F(2) + (((F((F(4))!))! / (F(4)!) + F((F(F((3)!) + 0!))))$
 24431 := $((((2 \times 4)! / (F(4)!) + F((F(F((3)!) + 1))))$
 24432 := $((-2) \times (4)!) - (((F(4))! \times (-F((3^2))))$
 24433 := $(F(2) - (((4)! - (4^{3!})) \times (3)!))$
 24434 := $(2 + ((F(4))! \times ((4^{3!}) - (4)!))$
 24435 := $((F(F((F(2) + (F(4))!))) \times F(F((F(4))!))) - (3!) \times 5$
 24436 := $((2 - (4)!) \times (F(F(4)) + ((3)!)!) + (F(6))!$
 24437 := $((-2) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F((4)!) - (3 \times F(7)))$
 24438 := $(((-F(2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F((F(4))^{F(3)})) - 8$
 24439 := $((-F(2) - (F(4))!) - (((F(4))! - F(F(3))) \times (-F(9))))$
 24440 := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4))!))) \times ((F(4))!)) - 40$
 24442 := $((-2) + (F((F(4))!))!) - (((F(4))! \times F(F((F(4))!)^2))$
 24443 := $(((-F(2) + ((F(4))!)) \times F((F(4) \times F(4)))) - 3$
 24444 := $(((-2) \times F((4)!) - ((F(4) + (4))!) / (-4))$
 24445 := $(-F(2) + (((F(4))! - F(F(F(4)))) \times F((4 + 5))))$
 24446 := $((-F(2) + ((4)! / 4)!) \times F((F(4) + (6))))$
 24448 := $(-2) + ((F(4))! \times ((4^{F(4)!}) - (F(8))))$
 24449 := $(2 + (F(((4)! + (4))) / (4 + 9)))$
 24452 := $((-2) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + ((F((4)!) - ((5 - F(2))!))$
 24453 := $((2^{F(4)!}) + (((4)! + (5)^3))$

- 24454 := (((-(F(2)) + ((F(4))!)) × F((4 + 5))) + F((F(4))!))
 24455 := -((F(2) + ((4)! × (-((4⁵) - 5))))))
 24456 := -(24) + (F((4 + 5)) × (6)!))
 24457 := ((F(2) - ((F(4))!)) - (((4)! + (-5) × (7)!)))
 24458 := -(F(2) + (((F(4))! × F((4 + 5))) - (F(8))))
 24459 := -(F((2 × 4)) - ((F(4))! × (-((5)! × F(9))))
 24460 := ((F(2) - F(F((F(4))!))) - (((F(4))! × (-F((F(6) + 0!))))))
 24461 := ((2 - F(F((F(4))!))) - (((F(4))! × (-F((F(6) + 1!))))))
 24462 := ((-2) + F((4)!)) + (((F(4))! + F(F(F(6)))) × (-2))
 24463 := (F(-(F(2) - (4)!)) + ((F(4))! × (F(F(6) - ((3)!!)))
 24464 := ((-2) × (F(F((4 + 4))) + 6)) + F((4)!))
 24466 := ((((-2) + F((4)!)) - F((F(4))!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(F(6))))
 24467 := (((2 + 4)! × F((F(4) + (6)))) - F(7))
 24468 := (((2 × F((4)! - (4))) - F(6)) + F(F(8)))
 24469 := ((-(2 × 4)) - F(4)) + ((6)! × F(9))
 24470 := ((F(2) + (4)) × ((F(F((F(4))!)) × F(F(7))) + 0!))
 24472 := (-((2 × 4)) - (((F(4))! × (-F((7 + 2))))))
 24473 := ((-F(2) - (F(4))!) + (F((-4) + F(7))) × ((3)!!))
 24474 := (((2 + 4)! × F((-4) + F(7))) - (F(4))!)
 24475 := (((-F(2) - F((F(4) × 4))) + ((7)!)) × 5)
 24476 := (F((-2) + (4)!)) + F(((4 × 7) - F(6)))
 24477 := ((F(2) + F(((4)! - F(F(4)))) + F((F(7) + (7))))
 24478 := (((2 + F((4)!)) - F((F(4) × 7))) - F(F(8)))
 24479 := -(F(2) + ((-(((4/4) - 7)))! × F(9)))
 24480 := (((24/4)! × F((8 + 0!)))
 24481 := (F(2) - (((4)!/4)! × (-F((8 + 1))))))
 24482 := ((F((-2) + (4)!)) + (F(4))!) + F((F(8) - F(2)))
 24483 := -(F(2) + (((F(4))!⁴) + F(F(8))) × F(3))
 24485 := ((-F(2) + F((4)!)) - (F(F(4)) × (F(F(8)) - (5))))
 24486 := (2 × (F(4) - ((4 - F(8)) × (6)!))
 24487 := ((-2) + F((4)!)) - ((F(F(4)) × F(F(8))) - F(7))
 24488 := (((2 × (F(4))!) + F((4)!)) - F(F(8))) - F(F(8))
 24489 := (((2 - (4)! × ((F(4))!)) + (((8)! + 9))
 24490 := 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! × F(9) + 0

$$\begin{aligned} 24491 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 1 \\ 24492 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 2 \\ 24493 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 3 \\ 24494 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 4 \\ 24495 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 5 \\ 24496 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 6 \\ 24497 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 7 \\ 24498 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 8 \\ 24499 &:= 2 + F(F(4)!) + F(4)!! \times F(9) + 9 \\ \\ 24505 &:= ((F((-2) + F(F((F(4))!)))) + (((5 + 0!)!)) \times 5) \\ 24513 &:= (-F(2) - (F((4 + 5) \times (-1 - ((3)!)!))) \\ 24514 &:= ((F(2) + ((F(4))!)! \times F((5 \times 1) + 4))) \\ 24516 &:= (2 - (F((4 + 5) \times (-1 - (6)!)!)) \\ 24524 &:= ((2 \times ((4)! - F(F(F((5 - 2)!)!)))) + F((4)!) \\ 24532 &:= (((2 \times ((F(4))!)! - (5)!) + F(F(F((3)!)!))) \times 2) \\ 24534 &:= ((2 \times (((4)! + (5)) - F(F(F((3)!)!)))) + F((4)!) \\ 24538 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (((5)! + (3)!) \times F(8))) \\ 24539 &:= (((2^{F(4)!}) - (5)) - (((3)!)! \times (-F(9)))) \\ 24544 &:= (-2) + ((F(4))! \times (-5) + (4^{F(4)!})) \\ 24548 &:= ((2 + ((F(4))!)! \times F((5 - 4) + 8))) \\ 24549 &:= (F(2) + (((F(4))! \times (5)!) + F(F(4))) \times F(9))) \\ 24552 &:= (-((F(2) - 4^5)) \times ((5 - F(2))!) \\ 24553 &:= (F(2) - (((F((F(4))!)!)/5) + (5)!) \times (-3)) \\ 24554 &:= (2 + (((F((F(4))!)!)/5) + (5)!) \times F(4)) \\ 24555 &:= ((F((2^4)) \times (5 \times 5)) - (5)!) \\ 24564 &:= (-2 + 4^{(-5 + F(6)!)}) \times F(4)! \\ 24568 &:= ((F(2) - ((4)! \times ((5)! + F(6)))) \times (-8)) \\ 24569 &:= (F(((2 + 4) + 5)) + ((6)! \times F(9))) \\ 24570 &:= ((F((2 \times 4) \times 5) \times (F(F(7)) + 0!)) \\ 24571 &:= (F(2) - (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-5) \times (F(F(7)) + 1)))) \\ 24572 &:= (2 + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (5 \times (F(F(7)) + F(2)))) \\ 24574 &:= (-2) + ((F(4))! \times ((-5) + F(7))^4)) \\ 24575 &:= (((F(2) + (4)) + (5)!) - (7)!) \times (-5) \\ 24582 &:= (((-2) + ((F(4))!)! + (5)) \times F((8 + F(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24584 &:= ((F(2) + ((4)! \times ((5)! + 8))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 24585 &:= ((F(F((F(2) + (F(4)!))) \times (5 \times F(8))) + (5)!) \\
 24586 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (F((-5) + F(8)))))) + ((6)!) \\
 24587 &:= ((2 - ((F(4)!))!) + (5 \times (F(8) + (7)!))) \\
 24593 &:= (((-F(2)) - (F(4)!)) + (5)!) - (-F(9) \times ((3)!)) \\
 24594 &:= (2 \times (-((4)!) + (((5)! - 9)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 24596 &:= (((F(2) \times (-4)) + (5)!) + (F(9) \times (6)!) \\
 24598 &:= (F(-((F(2) - (4)!))) - (((5)! \times F(9)) - F(8))) \\
 24614 &:= (-2) + ((4 + (6)!) \times F((1 + F((F(4)!)))) \\
 24616 &:= (((F(2) + F(4)) + (6)!) \times F((1 + F(6)))) \\
 24618 &:= (2 + ((4 + (6)!) \times F((1 + 8)))) \\
 24625 &:= ((-2) + F(((4)! - F(6))) \times 25) \\
 24626 &:= (F(F((2 \times 4))) - ((F(F(6)) - 2) \times (-6)!)) \\
 24628 &:= (2 + (((F(4)!))! \times (F(F(6)) - 2)) + F(F(8))) \\
 24633 &:= (-((F(2^4)) + ((6)! \times (-3))) \times F(F((3)!)) \\
 24634 &:= (-2) + (((F(4)! \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((3)!))!) - ((F(4)!))!) \\
 24635 &:= ((-F(2)) - (F((F(4)!))!)) - (-6 \times (F(F(F((3)!)) - (5)!)) \\
 24636 &:= (((2 + 4^6) + F((3)!)) \times 6) \\
 24638 &:= ((2 - ((F(4)!))!) - (((F(6)! - ((3)! \times F(F(8)))))) \\
 24642 &:= ((2 \times (F(4)^6)) + (F((4)!)/2)) \\
 24643 &:= ((-2) + F(F((F(4)!))) \times ((6^4) + F(F(3)))) \\
 24644 &:= ((-2) \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((F(F(6)) \times F((F(4)!)) + F((4)!))) \\
 24648 &:= ((F((F(2) + F((F(4)!))) \times (6)!) + (F((F(4)!)) \times F(8))) \\
 \\
 24650 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 0 \\
 24651 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 1 \\
 24652 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 2 \\
 24653 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 3 \\
 24654 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 4 \\
 24655 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 5 \\
 24656 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 6 \\
 24657 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 7 \\
 24658 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 8 \\
 24659 &:= F(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) \times (6! + 5) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

- 24663** := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4)!))) \times ((6)! + (6))) - (F(F((3)!))))$
- 24664** := $(2 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (66 \times F(F((F(4)!))))$
- 24669** := $((F(2) + F((F(4)!)) \times F(F(6))) + (((6)! \times F(9))))$
- 24676** := $(2 \times ((-((F(4)! + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-6))))$
- 24679** := $((F((F(2) + F((F(4)!))) \times (6)!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)))$
- 24682** := $(-2) + (((F(4)! + ((6)!) \times F((8 + F(2))))$
- 24683** := $((F(2) + (4)!) \times F((F(6) + 8))) + F((3)!)$
- 24684** := $(2 \times (((F(4)! + ((6)!) \times (F(8) - (4))))$
- 24686** := $((2 + (((F(4)!)! \times (-6)!) - 8)) / (-F(F(6))))$
- 24687** := $(((((2 \times 4)!) / F(F(6))) - (F(8))) \times F(7))$
- 24688** := $(2 \times ((F(F(4)) \times ((6)! - F(8))) + F(F(8))))$
- 24693** := $(F(2) + (((F(4)! + ((6)!) \times F(9)) + F((3)!)))$
- 24694** := $(((-2) + (F(4)^6) \times F(9)) - (4)!)$
- 24695** := $(-(((F(2) + (4)^6) + (F((F(9 - 5))!))!))$
- 24696** := $((2 + 4) \times (((6)! - F(9)) \times 6))$
- 24697** := $((((2 + 4) + (6)!) \times F(9)) + F(7))$
- 24698** := $(F(F((F(2) + (F(4)!))) \times (F(6) + 98))$
- 24714** := $(2 \times (((4)! \times F(F(7))) + F((-1 + F(F((F(4)!))))))$
- 24716** := $(-2) + (((F(4)!)! + 7) \times F((1 + F(6))))$
- 24718** := $((((2 + 4)!) + (7)) \times F((1 + 8)))$
- 24719** := $(F(2) + (((F(4)!)! + 7) \times F((1 \times 9))))$
- 24726** := $((2 + (4)!) \times (F(F(7)) - (2 - (6)!)))$
- 24736** := $((2^{F(F(4)!)}) - (F((7 + F(3))) \times (-6)!))$
- 24738** := $((2 + ((4)! \times (7^{F(3)}))) \times F(8))$
- 24744** := $((2 + (F(4) \times (7^{F(4)}))) \times (4)!)$
- 24745** := $(F(2) + ((4)! \times (7 + (4^5))))$
- 24746** := $(2 \times (((((F(4)!)! - F(7)) + ((F(4)!)! + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 24747** := $((F(2) + ((F(4)!)!) \times F((F(7) - (4)))) + F(F(7)))$
- 24748** := $(2 \times ((-F(4) + F(F(7))) + (((4)!) / (F(8)!)))$
- 24749** := $((2 + (4)!) + (7)!) + (F(4)^9)$
- 24752** := $((2^4) \times F(7)) \times ((5)! - F(2))$
- 24757** := $((((-2) \times F(F((F(4)!))) + ((7)!) \times 5) - F(F(7)))$
- 24764** := $((F((F(2) + (4)!)) - ((F(7) + (6)!))) / F(4))$
- 24766** := $(((-2) + (4)!) \times (F(7) - (6)!)) + (F(6)!)$

- 24768 := $(2 \times ((F(4)!)/7) + ((6)! \times 8))$
 24769 := $((2 + (4)!) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6)!)) - 9)$
 24772 := $(((-2) \times ((F(4)!)!) - F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) \times (-2)$
 24774 := $(2 \times (((F(4)!)! + F(F(7))) \times F(7)) - F(F(4)))$
 24776 := $(-2) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) + ((6)!)))$
 24777 := $(-F(2)) + (((F(4)!)! + F(F(7))) \times (F(7) + F(7)))$
 24782 := $((F(2) - F((4)!)) - ((-F(7)) \times F(F(8)))/2)$
 24783 := $((2 - F((4)!)) - ((-F(7)) \times F(F(8)))/F(3))$
 24784 := $(2 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) + ((F(F(7)) + 8) \times (F(4)!)))$
 24786 := $(2 \times (((F(4)!)! + (7 + F(F(8))) + ((6)!)))$
 24793 := $((F(2) + ((4)! \times F(7))) - (-F(9)) \times ((3)!))$
 24794 := $((2 + ((F(4)!)!) + 7) \times F(9) + F((F(4)!))$
 24795 := $((F(2) + (4)!) \times F((7 + 9))) + (5)!$
 24796 := $(2 \times (((F(4)!) \times (F(F(7)) + 9)) + F(F(F(6))))$
 24797 := $((F(2) + (4)) \times ((7)! - F(9))) - F(F(7))$
 24834 := $(((-2) \times F(F((F(4)!)!))) + F((F(8) - F(3)))) \times (F(4)!)$
 24837 := $((-F(2^4)) + F(F(8))) \times 3 - ((7)!)$
 24844 := $((F(2) + (F((F(4)!)!)) - (F(8) + (F((4)!)/F(4))))$
 24847 := $((F(2) - F(-(F(F(4)) - F(8)))) \times (-F(4)!)) - F(F(7))$
 24853 := $(2 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) + (F((F(8) - 5))) \times 3)$
 24864 := $(((-2) \times F((4)!) - ((8)! \times (-6)))/F(4)!)$
 24868 := $(2 \times (((F((4)!)/F(8)) - ((6)!)) + F(F(8))))$
 24875 := $((2 + ((F(4) \times F(8)) - (7)!)) \times (-5))$
 24878 := $(((-2) + (F((4)!)/F(8))) \times (-7)) + (8)!$
 24893 := $((-F(2)) + (F((F(4)!) \times ((8)!/9))) - F(F(F((3)!))))$
 24894 := $((F(2) - ((F(4)!)!) + 8) \times (-F(9))) + ((F(4)!))$
 24895 := $((2 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) - ((F(8) - ((9)!/5)!)))$
 24896 := $(2 + ((F((F(4)!) \times ((8)!/9)) - F(F(F(6))))$
 24916 := $((2 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) - ((9)!/(-(1 - 6)!)))$
 24924 := $((2 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) + (F(9)^2))) + ((F(4)!))$
 24925 := $((F(2) + (F(4)!))! - F((9 + F(2)))) \times 5$
 24933 := $(-F(2^4)) + ((F(9) + F(3)) \times ((3)!))$
 24938 := $(-((2^{F(F(4)!)}) - (F(9) \times ((3)! + F(8))))$
 24944 := $(-((2^{F(F(4)!)}) + ((-F(9)) \times ((F(4)!)) - ((F(4)!)))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 24947 &:= (F(2) + (((F(4))!)! \times F(9)) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))))) \\ 24948 &:= ((((-2) + (4)!) \times 9) \times (F(4))!) \times F(8)) \\ 24955 &:= ((F(2) - (4)!) \times ((-9) \times (5)!) - (5)) \\ 24956 &:= (F((F(2) + F((F(4))!))) \times ((9 + 5) + (6)!) \\ 24957 &:= (((2 - (-((F(F(4)) - 9)))!) \times (-5)) - F(F(7))) \\ 24958 &:= (-2) - ((F((F(4))!) - F(9)) \times ((5)! \times 8)) \\ 24967 &:= (((F(2)^{4!}) + F(9)) \times (6)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 24974 &:= ((2^{F(F(4)!)} + (F(9) \times (7 + ((F(4))!)!))) \\ 24975 &:= (((F(2) + (4)) \times 9) - (7)!) \times (-5) \\ 24976 &:= ((((-2) \times F((4)!)) / 9) - ((7)!) + (F(6))!) \\ 24984 &:= (((2 + 4)!) \times F(9)) + (F(8) \times (4)!) \\ 24990 &:= ((F((2 \times 4)) \times F(9)) \times (F(9) + 0!)) \\ 24991 &:= (F(2) - (F(F((F(4))!) \times (-F(9) \times (F(9) + 1)))))) \\ 24992 &:= (2 + (F(F((F(4))!) \times (F(9) + (F(9)^2)))))) \\ 24993 &:= ((F(2) + (F(F(4))^9)) - (-F(9)) \times ((3)!)!) \\ 24994 &:= ((F((F(2) + (4)!) - (9 + F(9))) / F(4)) \\ 24996 &:= (((F((2 \times 4)) \times F(9)) \times F(9)) + (6)!) \\ 24998 &:= ((2 + ((F(4))!)!) + (((F(9) \times F(9)) \times F(8)))) \\ 25056 &:= ((F((-2) + F(F((5 + 0!)))) - (5)) \times 6) \\ 25074 &:= -((F(2) - (-5) \times ((0! - (7)!) + (4)!)) \\ 25084 &:= (-2) - ((-5) - 0!) \times F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) \\ 25095 &:= ((-((2 + 5)!) + F(-((0! - 9))) \times (-5)) \\ 25097 &:= (2 - (5 \times (F(-((0! - 9))) - ((7)!))) \\ 25134 &:= ((F((-2) + F(F((5 + 1)))) + F((3)!) \times (F(4))!) \\ 25145 &:= (-F((2 \times 5)) + (((1 + (F(4))!)!) \times 5)) \\ 25175 &:= (((F(2) \times 5) - ((1 \times 7)!) \times (-5)) \\ 25176 &:= (F(2) + (-5) \times ((-1 - (7)!) + (6))) \\ 25178 &:= -((F(2) - ((5 \times ((1 \times 7)!) - F(8)))) \\ 25184 &:= (-F(2)) - (-5) \times ((-((1 - 8)))! - F(4)) \\ 25187 &:= (((F(2) \times 5) \times (-((1 - 8)))! - F(7)) \\ 25193 &:= (-((2 + 5)) + ((1 + F(9)) \times ((3)!)!) \\ 25194 &:= (-((F(2) - ((5)! \times (1 + F(9)))) \times (F(4))!) \\ 25196 &:= ((F(2) - (5)) + ((1 + F(9)) \times (6)!) \\ 25198 &:= (-2) + (((5)! \times (1 + 9)) \times F(8)) \\ 25201 &:= (F(2) + (5 \times (((2 + 0)!)! + 1)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25202 &:= (2 + (5 \times ((F(2) + ((0! + 2)!))!)) \\ 25203 &:= (-2) + (-5) \times (-F(2) - ((0! + (3)!))!) \\ 25204 &:= (-F(2)) - (-5) \times (F(2) + ((0! + (F(4)!))!)) \\ 25205 &:= ((F(2) + ((5 + 2)!)) \times 05) \\ 25206 &:= (F(2) + (-5) \times (-F(2) - ((0! + (6)!))!)) \\ 25216 &:= ((2^{-5+21}) - (F(6)!)) \\ 25235 &:= (((F(2) + ((5 + 2)!)) + (3!)) \times 5) \\ 25236 &:= ((25 + F((-2) + F(F((3)!)))) \times 6) \\ 25237 &:= (2 + (5 \times ((F(2) + (3!)) + (7)!)) \\ 25238 &:= (-2) + (5 \times (((F(2) + (3)!))! + 8)) \\ 25245 &:= (((F(2) + ((5 + 2)!)) + F((F(4)!)) \times 5) \\ 25247 &:= (2 + (-5) \times ((-F(2)) - F((F(4)!)) - ((7)!))) \\ 25255 &:= (F((2 \times 5)) + (((2 + 5)! \times 5)) \\ 25257 &:= ((2 + F((5 \times 2))) - (-5) \times (7!)) \\ 25265 &:= ((F((2 + 5)) + ((F(2) + (6)!))! \times 5) \\ 25267 &:= (2 - (-5) \times (F((F(2) + (6))) + ((7)!))) \\ 25275 &:= (((-2) - ((5 + 2)!)) - F(7)) \times (-5) \\ 25277 &:= (2 - (-5) \times ((2 + F(7)) + (7)!)) \\ 25296 &:= ((((-2) - (5!)) - 2) \times F(9)) \times (-6) \\ 25303 &:= (-2) - (-5) \times (F(F((3)!)) + ((0! + (3)!))!) \\ 25304 &:= (-F(2)) - (-5) \times (F(F((3)!)) + ((0! + (F(4)!))!)) \\ 25305 &:= (((2 + 5)! + F(F((3)!)) \times 05) \\ 25306 &:= (F(2) - (-5) \times (((3)! + 0!)! + F(F(6)))) \\ 25307 &:= (2 - (-5) \times (F(F((3)!)) + (07)!)) \\ 25319 &:= (F(F((2 + 5))) + ((3)! \times F(19))) \\ 25325 &:= ((-25) - (((3)! + F(2)))! \times (-5)) \\ 25326 &:= ((2 \times (5!)) + ((3)! \times F((-2) + F(F(6)))) \\ 25330 &:= ((25 + ((3)!))! \times F((F(3)! + 0!)) \\ 25336 &:= (((-2) + ((5)!^{F(3)})) - F((3)!)) + F(F(F(6))) \\ 25338 &:= ((-2) + (((5)!^{F(3)} - (3!)) + F(F(8))) \\ 25339 &:= (((2 + ((5)!^{F(3)})) + F(F(F((3)!)))) - 9) \\ 25342 &:= (-2) \times (((5 + F(3))! - F(((4)! - 2))) \\ 25343 &:= (-F(2) + (((5)! - F(F((3)!))) \times (F(F(4))^{F(3)})) \\ 25345 &:= (-((F(2) - ((5)!^{F(3)}))) + F(F((F(4) + (5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25346 &:= (((2 \times (5)!)^{F(3)})/4) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 25347 &:= ((F(2) + ((5)!^{F(3)})) + F((F(4) \times 7))) \\
 25348 &:= ((-2) + (((5)!^{F(3)} + (4))) + F(F(8))) \\
 25352 &:= (F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) + (((3)! + ((5)!^2))) \\
 25353 &:= (((2 + 5) + F(F(F((3)!)))) + ((5)!^{F(3)})) \\
 25354 &:= (F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) + ((F((3)!) + ((5)!^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 25356 &:= (((F(2) + (5)) \times F(F((3 + 5)))) - (F(6))!) \\
 25362 &:= -(((F((F(2) + (5))))! - ((3)! \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(2)))))) \\
 25363 &:= ((2 + 5) + (((3)! \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((3)!))!)) \\
 25364 &:= ((F((F(2) + (5))) - (F((3)!))!) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!)) \\
 25366 &:= ((-((F(2) - ((5)!^{F(3)}))) + F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 25369 &:= (-F(2)) + (-5 \times (((F((3)!))! / (-F(6))) - F(9))) \\
 25374 &:= ((-2) + (((5)! - F((3)!)) \times F(F(7)))) - ((F(4))!)) \\
 25376 &:= (((2 + (5)!) \times F(3)) \times F(7)) \times F(6) \\
 25379 &:= -((F(2) + (-5 \times ((F(3) + (7)!) + F(9)))))) \\
 25388 &:= ((2^5) + (((3)! \times F(F(8))) - (8)!)) \\
 25410 &:= (((F(2) + (5)!) \times F(F((F(4))!))) \times 10) \\
 25433 &:= ((-(((2 + (5)!)^{F(F(4))})) + (F((3)!))!) - 3) \\
 25434 &:= ((-(((2 + (5)!)^{F(F(4))})) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(4))) \\
 25436 &:= (-(((2 + (5)!) + (4))^{F(3)})) + (F(6))! \\
 25438 &:= (2 - (((5)! + F(F(4)))^{F(3)} - (8)!)) \\
 25439 &:= (-F(2) + (((5)! \times F((F(4))!)) - (((3)!!) \times (-F(9)))) \\
 25440 &:= ((F(F((2 + 5))) - F(F((F(4))!))) \times ((4 + 0)!)) \\
 25441 &:= (F(2) + (-((5)!) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - F(F(((F(4))! + 1)))))) \\
 25442 &:= (2 + (-((5)!) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - F(F(((F(4))! + F(2)))))) \\
 25444 &:= ((-(((2 + (5)!)^{F(F(4))})) + (F((F(4))!))!) + F((F(4))!)) \\
 25456 &:= ((2 \times ((5)! + (F((F(4))!)^5))) - (F(6))! \\
 25457 &:= (F(F((2 + 5))) + ((4)! - (-5 \times (7)!)) \\
 25464 &:= (F(2) + ((-5 \times F(-((F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))))) + F((4)!)) \\
 25465 &:= (((-F(2) + ((5)!^{F(F(4))})) + F(F(F(6)))) + (5)!) \\
 25466 &:= (((F(2) + (5)!) \times (-((F(4) - F(6))))!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 25469 &:= ((2 + F((-5) + F(F((F(4))!)))) + (((6)! \times F(9))) \\
 25473 &:= (((2 \times F((5 \times F(4)))) - 7) \times F(F((3)!)) \\
 25474 &:= (((-2) - (5)!) \times ((4)! - F(F(7)))) - ((4)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25475 &:= (((F(2) + (54)) + (7)!) \times 5) \\ 25477 &:= (2 + (5 \times (F((F(4) + (7))) + ((7)!)))) \\ 25486 &:= (((-(2 - 5)) \times ((4)!) / (F(8)!) - F(F(F(6)))) \\ 25487 &:= ((F(2) - (-5) \times (((F(4)!)! + 8))) \times 7) \\ 25488 &:= ((2 - (5)!) \times (((F(4)!) + (F(8))) \times (-8))) \\ 25494 &:= (-((F(2) - (5^{F(4)}) \times F(9)))) \times (F(4)!) \\ 25496 &:= ((((-2) + (5)!) \times (4)!) \times 9) + F(6) \\ 25498 &:= ((-2) - (5)!) \times ((4)! - F((F(9) - F(8)))) \\ 25532 &:= ((F(2) \times (-5^5)) + F((F(F((3)!) + 2))) \\ 25533 &:= ((F(2) - (5^5)) + F((F(3) + F(F((3)!)))) \\ 25534 &:= ((2 - (5^5)) + F(-(F(F(3)) - ((4)!)))) \\ 25536 &:= (((2^5) + (5)!) \times F((3)!) \times F(F(6))) \\ 25567 &:= ((-((F(2) + (5)!) \times (5)!) + (F(6)!) - F(F(7))) \\ 25573 &:= (-((F((2 + 5)) - (5)!) \times (F(F(7)) + (3)!)) \\ 25577 &:= (((2 + 5)!) \times 5) + F((7 + 7)) \\ 25578 &:= ((-((F(2) - ((5)! \times (5)!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\ 25583 &:= (((2 + (5)!) \times (5)!) + F(F(8))) - 3 \\ 25584 &:= (((2 + (5)!) \times (5)!) + F(F(8))) - F(F(4)) \\ 25586 &:= (((-(F(2) - (5))))! \times F(((5)!/8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 25620 &:= ((2 \times F(((5)!/F(6)))) \times F(F(((2 + 0)!)!)) \\ 25630 &:= (((-2) + (5)!) - F(6)) \times F(F(((3)! + 0!)) \\ 25632 &:= (((F(2) + (5)))! - F(6)) \times ((3)!^2) \\ 25633 &:= (((F((F(2) + (5))))! + F(F(F(6)))) / ((3)!/3) \\ 25634 &:= (((F((F(2) + (5))))! + F(F(F(6)))) / F(3) + F(F(F(4)))) \\ 25636 &:= (2 \times ((F(((5)!/F(6))) \times F(F((3)!)) + F(6))) \\ 25638 &:= ((-(2 \times 5)) \times (6)!) + (3 \times F(F(8))) \\ 25643 &:= ((2 \times 5) - ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(4)!)!)) / (-F(3)))) \\ 25644 &:= (((2 \times F(((5)!/F(6)))) \times F(F((F(4)!)!)) + (4)!) \\ 25645 &:= (((2 + 5)!) + F((F(6) + F(4)))) \times 5 \\ 25647 &:= (2 + (5 \times (F((F(6) + F(4))) + ((7)!)))) \\ 25648 &:= (-2) + (-5) \times (((F(6)!) + ((F(4)!)!) / (-8))) \\ 25652 &:= ((F(F((2 + 5))) - F(F(6))) \times ((5)! + F(2))) \\ 25664 &:= (2 + ((5 + F(F(6))) \times F(-(F(6) - (4)!)))) \\ 25673 &:= ((-((F(2) + (5)!) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(7)))) + F(F((3)!))) \\ 25674 &:= (2 \times ((F((-5) + F(F(6)))) \times F(7)) + (F(4)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 25704 := -(((F(2) - (5)!) × ((7 - 0!)^{F(4)})))
25723 := -(2) + (((5 × 7)²) × F(F((3)!)))
25724 := -(F(2)) + (((5 × 7)²) × F(F((F(4)!))))
25733 := -((2 + 5)) - (((F(7)!)/(F((3)!))!)/(-3)!))
25734 := -((F(2) + (5))) - (((F(7)!)/(F((3)!))!)/(-F(4)!))
25735 := (((2 × F(5 + F(7)))) - F(F((3)!))) × 5
25736 := ((F(2) - (5)) + (((F(7)!)/(3)!)/(F(6)!)))
25738 := -(2) + (((-(5)!) × (F(7)!)/((3)!)/(-8)!))
25742 := ((2 + (5)!) × (((7)!/(4)! + F(2)))
25743 := -((2 - 5)) - (-(((F(7)!)/(F(4)!)))/(F((3)!)!))
25744 := -(2) × (F((5 + F(7))) - (F(4)!/F(4)))
25746 := ((F(2) + (5)) + (((F(7)!)/(F(4)!)/(F(6)!)))
25748 := (F((F(2) + (5)))) + (((F(7)!)/(F(4)!)/(8)!))
25764 := (-((F(2) - (5))))! + (((F(7)!)/(F(6)!)/(F(4)!)))
25765 := (((F(2) - (5)!) - (7)!) + (6)) × (-5)
25767 := ((F(-(2 - 5)) + F(7)) × F(F(6))) + ((7)!)
25777 := ((F(-(F(2) - (5 + 7)))) × F(F(7))) + ((7)!)
25787 := (((F(2) × (5)!) - F(7)) × (8 + F(F(7))))
25799 := -(F(2)) - (-((5)!) × (F(F(7)) - (9 + 9)))
25805 := (-((F(2) + (5)!)) - ((8 - 0)!) × (-5))
25830 := ((2 × 5) × (F((F(8) - 3)) - 0!))
25833 := -((F(F((2 + 5))) - F(F(8)))) - (-(((3)!!) × F(F((3)!)))
25834 := (((2 × 5) × F((F(8) - 3))) - (F(4)!))
25839 := -(F(2)) + (((5 × 8) + ((3)!!) × F(9))
25863 := (F(F((2 + 5))) × (F(8) + ((6)!/F((3)!)))
25864 := ((-2) - (5)!) × (F(8) - F(F((F(F(6))/F(4))))))
25866 := ((-2) + ((5)! × 8)) × (6 + F(F(6)))
25872 := (((F(2) × (5)!) - 8) × (F(F(7)) - 2))
25873 := (F(2) + (((5)! - 8) × (F(F(7)) - F(3))))
25874 := (2 + (((5)! - 8) × (F(F(7)) - F(F(4))))))
25877 := (((-2) - (5)!) × (F(8) - F(F(7)))) + F(7)
25893 := ((F(2) - ((5)! × 8)) × (-9 × 3))
25907 := -((F((2 + 5)) - ((9)!/(0! + F(7))))))
25914 := -(((F(2) + (5)) + ((9)!/(-14))))
25917 := ((2 - 5) - ((9)!/(-1 - F(7))))

$$25920 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 0$$

$$25921 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 1$$

$$25922 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 2$$

$$25923 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 3$$

$$25924 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 4$$

$$25925 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 5$$

$$25926 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 6$$

$$25927 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 7$$

$$25928 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 8$$

$$25929 := (F(2) + 5)! \times (F(9) + 2) + 9$$

$$25933 := (F((2 + 5)) + ((F(9) + F(3)) \times ((3)!)))$$

$$25936 := ((2 - ((5)! \times (-9 \times 3))) \times F(6))$$

$$25937 := (((F(2) - (5)!) - ((9)!/F(3)))/(-7))$$

$$25938 := (-(((F(2) - (5)!) \times F(9))) - (-F(3) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$25942 := ((F(2) - (5)!) \times ((-9) \times (4)! - 2))$$

$$25943 := (((F(2) + ((5)! \times 9)) \times (4)!) - F(F(3)))$$

$$25944 := (((F(2) \times (5)!) \times 9) \times (4)!) + (4)!$$

$$25946 := (-(((F(2) \times (5)!) - ((9)!/(4)!))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$25947 := ((F((F(2) + (5))))!) + (-9) \times F(((4)! - (7))))$$

$$25948 := (((2 - (5)!) + ((9)!/(4)!)) + F(F(8)))$$

$$25954 := ((F((F(2) + (5))))!) + (F(9) - ((5)!^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$25956 := (((2 \times (5)!) - F(9)) \times ((5)! + (6)))$$

$$25972 := (-2) - (-(((5)! - 9)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(2)))$$

$$25973 := (-F(2)) + (((5)! - 9) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(3))))$$

$$25974 := -((((F(2) + (5)))! - (9 + (7)!)) \times (F(4)!))$$

$$25975 := (((F(2) + (5)!) + F(9)) + (7)!) \times 5$$

$$25992 := ((2 + ((F(-((5 - 9))))!)!) \times (F(9) + 2))$$

$$26024 := (((-2) + (6)!) \times F(F(((0! + 2)!))) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$26043 := ((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((-0!) + ((F(4)!!) \times F(F((3)!))))$$

$$26044 := ((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((0! - ((F(4)!!) \times F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$26046 := ((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((0! - ((F(4)!!) \times (-F(F(6)))))$$

$$26063 := ((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) + (-0!) + (F(F(6)) \times ((3)!))$$

$$26064 := (F((2 \times 6)) \times (0! + ((6)!/4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26066 &:= (F(F((2+6))) + (F(F(06)) \times (6)!)) \\ 26068 &:= (2 - ((-(6)!) \times F(F(06))) - F(F(8))) \\ 26073 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(07) + (3)!)) \\ 26074 &:= (((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) + 0!) + F((F(7) + (F(4)!))) \\ 26086 &:= (-((F(2) - (((6)! + 0!) \times F(8)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 26088 &:= ((F(2) + (((6)! + 0!) \times F(8))) + F(F(8))) \\ 26136 &:= ((2 + F((F(6) + 1))) \times ((3)! + (6)!)) \\ 26158 &:= (F((2 + F(F(6)))) - ((-1 + (5)!) \times F(8))) \\ 26207 &:= (-F(2) - (((F(6)!)/(-20)) \times F(7))) \\ 26243 &:= -((F(2) - ((6^2) \times (F(4)^{3!}))) \\ 26287 &:= ((2 \times (F(6)!) + (F((-2) + F(8))) \times (-F(7))) \\ 26308 &:= (2 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(((3+0)!)!)/(-F(8)))) \\ 26327 &:= (F((2 + F(F(6)))) - ((F((3)!) + 2) \times F(F(7))) \\ 26334 &:= (((2 \times F((F(6) \times F(3)))) - ((3)!)! \times F(F((F(4)!))) \\ 26337 &:= ((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F((3)!) \times (((3)!)! + F(7))) \\ 26338 &:= (2 \times (((F(F(6)) + ((3)!)!) \times 3) + F(F(8))) \\ 26343 &:= (((F((-F(2) + F(F(6)))) \times 3) + F((4)!) - (F((3)!)!)) \\ 26344 &:= (((-F(2) - F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))))) \times (-4) - ((F(4)!)!)) \\ 26345 &:= -((F((2 + F(6))) \times (F(F(3) + (-4) \times (5)!))) \\ 26349 &:= (-F(2) + (((6)! + F(((3)! + (4)))) \times F(9))) \\ 26352 &:= ((F(2) \times (6^3)) \times ((5)! + 2)) \\ 26353 &:= (F(2) - (-((6^3) \times ((5)! + F(3)))) \\ 26354 &:= (2 + ((6^3) \times ((5)! + F(F(4)))) \\ 26365 &:= ((F(F((F(2) + (6)))) + ((F(F(3) + 6))!) \times 5) \\ 26369 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (3 + ((F(6)!)/(-9))) \\ 26372 &:= (((2 \times (F(6)!) + F(F((3)!)) - (F(F(7))^2)) \\ 26375 &:= (((((F(2) + (6))!) + F(3) + F(F(7))) \times 5) \\ 26376 &:= ((2 \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(3) - ((7)!/F(6)))) \\ 26384 &:= (2 \times (-F(6) - (((3)!)! - (8)!/F(4))) \\ 26390 &:= ((2 \times F((F(6) + (3)!)) \times (F(9) + 0!)) \\ 26393 &:= ((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (((F((3)!)!)/(-9)) - F(F((3)!))) \\ 26394 &:= (2 \times (((F(6)!) - ((3)!)!) - 9)/F(4)) \\ 26395 &:= (F((2 + F(F(6)))) - ((3)! \times F((9 + 5)))) \\ 26402 &:= (F(F((2 + 6))) + (F((4)!)/(0! + 2))) \\ 26403 &:= ((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F((4)!)/(0 - 3))) \end{aligned}$$

- 26404** := $((2 + F(F(F(6)))) - (F((4)!)/(0 - F(4))))$
26414 := $(2 \times (((F(6)!/F(4)) - F(F((1 + (F(4)!))))))$
26424 := $(((((F(2) + (6)))! + F((4)!)/2) + ((F(4)!))!)$
26433 := $(F(2) + (((6)! + F(((4)! - (3)!))) \times F((3)!))$
26434 := $(2 + (((6)! + F(((4)! - (3)!))) \times F((F(4)!)))$
26436 := $((F((F(2) + F(6))) + (F((4)!)/3)) + F(F(F(6))))$
26438 := $(((-2) + F((-6) + (4)!)) \times (3)!) + F(F(8))$
26443 := $((F((2 + F(F(6)))) - (F(4)!) - (F((4)!/F(F((3)!))))$
26444 := $((2 \times F(F(6))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F((4)!)/(-F(4))))$
26445 := $-(((F(2) - (6^{F(4)})) \times (F(4) + (5)!))$
26446 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) + (-F(4) - (F((4)!/F(F(6))))$
26447 := $(((((F(2) + (6)))!/4) \times F(F((F(4)!))) - F(7))$
26448 := $(-2) + ((F((-6) + (4)!)) \times (F(4)!) + F(F(8)))$
26449 := $(F(2) - (((6)! - (4)!) \times (-4) - F(9)))$
26456 := $((-2) \times (F(F(6)) - ((F(4)!)^5))) + F(F(F(6)))$
26458 := $(-2) + (((F(6)!/F(F(4))^5) \times F(8))$

26460 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 0$
26461 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 1$
26462 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 2$
26463 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 3$
26464 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 4$
26465 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 5$
26466 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 6$
26467 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 7$
26468 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 8$
26469 := $(F(2) + 6)!/4 \times F(F(6)) + 9$

26472 := $(2 \times ((6 + (F((4)!)/(-7))) \times (-2)))$
26474 := $((-F(2) - F(F(6))) + ((F((4)!)/(-7)) \times (-4)))$
26484 := $(((((F(2) + (6)))!/4) \times F(8)) + ((4)!))$
26486 := $((((-2) - (6)!) \times 4) - F(F(8))) + (F(6)!)$
26487 := $((F((2 \times F(6))) \times F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((8)!/(-7)))$
26488 := $(((-(2 \times 6)) \times F((4)!)/(-F(8))) - 8)$
26493 := $(F(2) + (((6)! - (4)!) \times (F(9) + 3)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26494 &:= (2 + (((6)! - (4)) \times (F(9) + F(4)))) \\
 26495 &:= ((-(F(2)) + (F(6))!) - (((4)!^{F(9-5)})) \\
 26497 &:= ((F(2) + (F(6))!) - ((4)!^{F(-9+F(7))})) \\
 26526 &:= ((F((-2) + F(F(6)))) - ((5)! \times (-2))) \times 6 \\
 26539 &:= ((2 + F(F(F(6)))) + (((5^3!) - F(9)))) \\
 26544 &:= (((F((2 \times F(6))) + (5)!) \times (4)!) - ((4)!) \\
 26546 &:= ((2 \times ((6^5) + (4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 26548 &:= ((-2) - F(F(6))) + ((5^{F(4)!}) + F(F(8))) \\
 26554 &:= (((2 \times 6) \times (5^5) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 26560 &:= (-2) - ((6 - (5)!) \times F(F((F(6) - 0!)))) \\
 26561 &:= (-(F(2)) - ((6 - (5)!) \times F(F((6 + 1)))) \\
 26562 &:= (F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \times ((5)! - ((6/2)!)) \\
 26563 &:= ((F(F((2 + 6))) + (5^6) - F((3)!)) \\
 26564 &:= ((-(F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (-((5^6) + (F(4))!)) \\
 26566 &:= ((2 - (6)!) \times ((5 - F(F(6))) - F(F(6))) \\
 26567 &:= (-((F(2) - (6))) + (((5)! - (6)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 26568 &:= (((-((2 - 6)))! \times ((5)! + F((F(6) + 8)))) \\
 26569 &:= (((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) + (5^{(-6+9)!})) \\
 26570 &:= (((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((5^{7-0!})) \\
 26573 &:= ((2 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((5^{F(7-3)!})) \\
 26575 &:= (((F((2 + F(6))) \times 5) + ((7)!) \times 5) \\
 26577 &:= (2 + (((-6) + (5)!) \times F(F(7))) + F(7)) \\
 26580 &:= (-((2 - 6)) \times (-((5)!) + F((F(8) - 0!)))) \\
 26603 &:= (-((F(2) - (6)!) \times (F((F(6) + 0!) + 3)) \\
 26624 &:= (-((2^{F(6)})) + (((F(6))! \times (-2))/(-F(4)))) \\
 26625 &:= (((-2) \times (6)!) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) \times 5 \\
 26633 &:= (((2 \times (F(6))!) - F(F(6))) - ((3)!)!)/3 \\
 26634 &:= (((F(2) + (6 \times 6)) \times ((3)!)! - (F(4))!) \\
 26635 &:= (((F(2) + (6 \times 6)) \times ((3)!)! - (5)) \\
 26639 &:= -((F(2) + ((6)! \times (-((6 - 3)) - F(9)))) \\
 \\
 26640 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!)/F(4) + 0 \\
 26641 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!)/F(4) + 1 \\
 26642 &:= (2 \times F(6)! - 6!)/F(4) + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$26643 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 3$$

$$26644 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 4$$

$$26645 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 5$$

$$26646 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 6$$

$$26647 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 7$$

$$26648 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 8$$

$$26649 := (2 \times F(6)! - 6!) / F(4) + 9$$

$$26656 := ((2 \times ((6)! + (F(6)^5))) - (F(6))!)$$

$$26664 := (((F(2) + (6 \times 6)) \times (6)!) + (4)!))$$

$$26674 := (F((F(2) + F(6))) + ((6)! \times (F(7) + (4)!)))$$

$$26678 := (((2 - (6)!) \times (6 + F(7))) + (8)!))$$

$$26714 := ((-2) - (6)!) \times ((F(7) \times (-1)) - (4)!))$$

$$26724 := (((F(2) - (F(6))!) + F(F(7))) \times (-2)) / F(4))$$

$$26730 := -((F((2 + F(6))) \times ((F(F(7)) - ((3)!)!) + 0!)))$$

$$26733 := ((F(2) - ((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) \times (3)!) \times F(F((3)!)))$$

$$26743 := ((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F((3)!))))$$

$$26744 := ((F((2 + F(F(6)))) - F(F(7))) + ((F((F(4)!)!) / (-4)!)))$$

$$26745 := ((2 \times (6)!) + (((7)! + F(F((F(4)!)!))) \times 5))$$

$$26748 := ((((-F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times (F(4)!) - (8)!))$$

$$26749 := (F((2 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(7)) - F(F((F(4)!)!))) \times 9))$$

$$26753 := ((-2) \times (6)!) - (F(F(7)) \times (-((5)!) - F(F(3))))$$

$$26754 := ((((-2) - F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times (5)!) - (F(4)!))$$

$$26755 := ((((-2) - F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times (5)!) - (5))$$

$$26760 := ((((-2) - F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times ((6 - 0)!))$$

$$26764 := ((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (7 \times ((6)! - (4)!)))$$

$$26766 := (((2 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times 6 - (F(6))!)$$

$$26768 := (((2 \times (6)!) + F(F(7))) \times (F(6) + 8))$$

$$26774 := ((((-2) + (-((F(6) - F(7))))!) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(4)!)!))$$

$$26776 := (((((2 \times F(6))!) / (F(7)!) - F(7)) \times F(6))$$

$$26778 := ((2 \times (-6) - F((F(7) + (7)))) + (8)!))$$

$$26782 := (2 \times (((6)! - (7)!) + F((F(8) + F(2))))$$

$$26783 := (-2) + (((6)! - F(F(7))) \times F((8 + F(3))))$$

$$26785 := -((F((2 + F(6))) \times (F(F(7)) - (((8 - 5)!)!)))$$

$$26786 := (((F(-((2 - 6))) \times (7)!) + F(F(8))) + ((6)!))$$

- 26788 := $((-((F(2 \times 6)) - (7!)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(8)))$
- 26804 := $((-(2^6) + F((F(8) - 0!))) \times 4)$
- 26806 := $((2 \times (F(6) - F((F(8) - 0!)))) + (F(6))!)$
- 26808 := $((F(2) + (6!)) \times (F(8) + 0!)) + F(F(8))$
- 26823 := $((F(2) + ((6 \times F(8))^2)) + F(F(F((3)!))))$
- 26824 := $((2 + ((6 \times F(8))^2)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
- 26833 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(8)) - F(3))/(-3)!))$
- 26834 := $(((-2) - F(F(6))) + ((8)!/3)) \times F(F(4))$
- 26835 := $-((F((-F(2)) + F(F(6)))) - (((8)!/(3!) \times 5)))$
- 26836 := $(((-2) + (F(6) \times F(8)))^{F(3)} - (6)!)$
- 26838 := $((-2) \times F(F(6))) + (((8)!/(-3)) + (8)!)$
- 26839 := $((((-2) \times (F(6))!) + (F(8)))/(-3) - F(9))$
- 26840 := $(-2) \times (F(F(6)) - (((8)!/F(4)) + 0!))$
- 26842 := $((2 - F(F(6))) + ((8)!/F(4))) \times 2$
- 26843 := $((-2) \times (F(6) - ((8)!/F(4)))) - F(F((3)!))$
- 26844 := $(2 \times (6 + (((8)!/F(4)) - (4)!))$
- 26846 := $((-2) \times (F(F(6)) - ((8)!/F(4)))) + F(6)$
- 26847 := $(F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) + ((8^4) + (7)!))$
- 26848 := $(-2) \times (F(6) - (((8)!/F(4)) - 8))$
- 26853 := $(((-F(2)) - F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(8) \times (5)!)) + (F((3)!))!)$
- 26854 := $(((-2) \times ((F(6))! + (F(8)))) + (5)!)/(-F(4))$
- 26856 := $((2 + (F(6))!) - F(F(8))) - ((5)! \times F(F(6)))$
- 26857 := $(((-2) - (F(6))!) - F(F(8))) + (5^7)$
- 26866 := $((-F(2)) + ((F(6))!/F(8))) \times (F(6) + (6))$
- 26867 := $((((2 - 6) \times (8)!)/(-6)) - F(7))$
- 26873 := $(((-2) \times (F(6))!) + (F(8)))/(-F((7 - 3)))$
- 26874 := $((2 \times (F(6))!)/(F(8)/7) - (F(4))!)$
- 26875 := $((2 \times (F(6))!)/(F(8)/7) - (5))$
- 26876 := $((2 \times ((6 - (8)!)) \times (-7))/F(F(6)))$
- 26877 := $((-2) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(8)))) - (F(7) - (7)!)$
- 26878 := $((-2) + (F(6))!) - (((8)! \times 7)/F(8))$
- 26881 := $(F(2) - ((-6) \times (8)!)/(8 + 1))$
- 26882 := $(2 - ((-6) \times (8)!)/(8 + F(2)))$
- 26883 := $((F(2) + F(6)) + (8)! + (8)!)/3$
- 26884 := $((2 \times 6) + (8)! + (8)!)/F(4)$

- 26887 := (((-2) × (F(6))!) - (F(8)))/(F(8)/(-7))
- 26892 := ((F(2) × 6) × (((8)!/9) + 2))
- 26893 := (F(2) - (-6) × (((8)!/9) + F(3)))
- 26894 := (((2 × (F(6))!) + (8 + F(9)))/F(4))
- 26896 := ((2 × F(6)) + (((8)!/9) × 6))
- 26897 := ((-F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(8)) - ((F(9) - (7)!))))
- 26898 := (((((F(2) + (6))!) + F(F(8))) - F(9)) + F(F(8)))
- 26903 := (((2 × ((F(6))! + F(9))) + 0!)/3)
- 26907 := (F((2 × F(6))) + (((9)!/(0! + F(7))))
- 26914 := ((2 × (F(F(F(6))) - 9)) + ((1 + (F(4))!))!)
- 26923 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) - (9 - ((F(2) + (3)!))!))
- 26926 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) + (((9 - 2)! - (6)))
- 26927 := -((F((2 × F(6))) - (((9)! + 2)/F(7))))
- 26931 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) + (((9 - F(3))! - 1)))
- 26932 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) - (((9 - F(3))! × (-F(2))))
- 26933 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) + (((9 - F(3))! + F(F(3))))
- 26934 := (2 - 69)^{F(3)} × F(4)!
- 26936 := ((F(-(2 - 6)) + F(9)) × (F((3)! + ((6)!)))
- 26941 := (((2 × F(F(F(6)))) + 9) + (((F(4))! + 1))!)
- 26942 := (F((-F(2) + F(F(6)))) - ((-F(9) - (F((F(4))!))!)/2))
- 26943 := (((2 × (F(6))!)/9) + F(F((F(4))!))) × 3
- 26944 := (((2^{F(6)}) + (9 × ((F(4))!))!)) × 4
- 26947 := (((2 + (6)!) × (F(9) + F(4))) + F(F(7)))
- 26954 := (2 × (((F(6))! - (9 - (5)!))/F(4)))
- 26964 := (2 × ((F(6) + F(9)) + ((F(6))!/F(4))))
- 26966 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) - (-F(9) - ((F(6))!/F(6))))
- 26967 := (((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((7)!)
- 26974 := (F(2) + (((6)! + 9) × (F(7) + (4)!)))
- 26976 := ((((-2) × F(6)) × F(9)) + (7)!) × 6
- 26987 := ((2 × F(F(F(6)))) + (((F(9) + F(8)) + (7)!)))
- 27027 := (-F(2) - (((F(F(7)) - 0!)/(-2)) × F(F(7))))
- 27032 := (2 × ((7 - F((-0!) + F(F(3)!))) × (-2)))
- 27034 := (2 + ((7 - F((-0!) + F(F(3)!))) × (-4)))
- 27044 := ((F((-F(2) + F((7 + 0!)))) - 4) × 4)

- 27047** := ((F((-F(2)) + F((7 + 0!)))) × 4) - F(7)
27060 := ((-((2 - 7)) - 0!) × F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))
27064 := ((-F(2)) - F(((F(7) - 0!) + F(6)))) × (-4)
27072 := ((F((2 × 7)) - 0!) × 72)
27075 := (((2 - (7)!) - F((0! + F(7)))) × (-5))
27084 := ((-((F(2) - (7))) + F(-((0! - F(8)))))) × 4)
27085 := ((F((2 × 7)) + (-((0! - 8)))!) × 5)
27087 := -((((2^{F(7)}) + 0!) - (8)!) + (7)!)
27088 := ((-((2^{F(7)})) - (-((0! - 8)))!) + (8)!)
27143 := (-F(2)) - (F((F(7) + 1)) × ((4)! × (-3)))
27144 := ((F((2 × 7)) × ((1 × 4)!) × F(4))
27145 := (F(2) - ((F(F(7)) - 1) × (F(4) - (5)!)))
27225 := (((2 + F(7))²) × (F(2) + (5)!))
27230 := (-((2^{F(7)})) - (-2) × F((F(F((3)!) + 0!)))
27245 := (((F(F((F(2) + (7)))))/2) - ((4)!) × 5)
27251 := (((-2) + F(F(7))) - 2) × ((5)! - 1))
27254 := (((-2) + F(F(7))) × (-2) + (5)!) - 4)
27255 := (((2 + F(F(7))) + 2) × ((5)! - (5)))
27258 := ((-2) + F(7)) × ((-2) + (5)!) × F(8))
27263 := (2 + (F(F(7)) × ((-((F(2) - (6))))!) - 3))
27264 := ((-2) + F((F(7) - F(2)))) × (F(6) × (4)!)
27324 := -((((F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) - (3)!)²) - F((4)!))
27325 := ((-((F(2) + (7))) - (F(F(F((3)!)))/(-2))) × 5)

27330 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 0
27331 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 1
27332 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 2
27333 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 3
27334 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 4
27335 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 5
27336 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 6
27337 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 7
27338 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 8
27339 := (2⁷)^{F(3)} + F(F(F(3!))) + 9

$$\begin{aligned}
 27342 &:= (((-2) + F(F(7))) + ((F((3)!))! / F(4))) \times 2 \\
 27343 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(7)) + ((F((3)!))! / F(4)))) - 3) \\
 27344 &:= (2 \times (((F(7) + (3)!) \times ((F(4)!))! - F((F(4)!)))) \\
 27345 &:= (((F(F((F(2) + (7)))) - F((3)!)) / F(F(4))) \times 5) \\
 27346 &:= (2 \times (-7 - (((3)! \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))))) \\
 27347 &:= ((2 \times (7)!) + (((3)! \times (4)!) - F(7))) \\
 27349 &:= ((2 - F(7)) + (((3)! \times (4 + F(9)))) \\
 27352 &:= (-2) \times (F(7) - ((-3) + (5)!)^2)) \\
 27353 &:= ((F(2) - F(7)) + ((F(F(F(3)!)) \times (-5)) / (-F(3)))) \\
 27354 &:= -((((F(2) - (7)!) \times (3)!) + ((5)! \times (4)!)) \\
 27355 &:= ((((-2) + F(F(7))) - 3) \times (5)!) - (5) \\
 27358 &:= (-2) - (((7)! \times ((3)! - (5)!)) / F(8)) \\
 27359 &:= (-((F(2) + (7)!) - (((3)! \times (-5 \times 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27360 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 0 \\
 27361 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 1 \\
 27362 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 2 \\
 27363 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 3 \\
 27364 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 4 \\
 27365 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 5 \\
 27366 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 6 \\
 27367 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 7 \\
 27368 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 8 \\
 27369 &:= 2 \times (F(7) + 3!) \times 6! + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27374 &:= (2 \times (7 + (((3)! \times (F(7) + (F(4)!)))) \\
 27376 &:= ((-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (-F(3) + ((F(7) - F(6))!)) \\
 27378 &:= ((F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (-3) + ((F(7) - 8)!) \\
 27384 &:= (((-((F(2) - (7))))! \times 38) + ((4)!) \\
 27386 &:= ((2 \times F(7)) + (38 \times (6)!) \\
 27394 &:= (F((2 + 7)) + (((3)! \times (F(9) + (4)))) \\
 27425 &:= ((F((2 \times 7)) + ((F(4)!))! \times 25) \\
 27434 &:= (-2) + (((F(7) + (F(4)!))³ \times 4) \\
 27435 &:= (((2 \times 7) - (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) / (-F(3)))) \times 5) \\
 27436 &:= (((2 \times 7) + (4)!) \times (F(3) + (6)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 27437 := ((F((2 + F(7))) × ((4)! + F(F((3)!)))) - F(7))
- 27439 := (-F(2) + (((7^{F(4)}) × ((3)!)/9))
- 27444 := (((-2) × F(F(7))) + ((F(4) + (4)))! × (F(4))!)
- 27445 := ((F((2 + F(7))) × (F(F((F(4))!)) + (4)!)) - (5))
- 27446 := (((2 × 7)⁴) - (4)! - F(F(F(6))))
- 27448 := ((-F(2) + F(F(7))) - (((F(4))!)⁴ × (-F(8))))
- 27449 := (F((-2) + F(7))) + (((F(4))!)! × (4 + F(9)))
- 27464 := (((2 × 7)⁴) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F(4))!
- 27468 := ((2 × (((7)! + F((4)!)) / (-F(6)))) + (8)!)
- 27470 := (((2 × 7)⁴) - F(F((7 + 0!))))
- 27472 := (2 × ((-F(F(7))) - (F((F(4))!)! + (F(F(7))²)))
- 27473 := ((((-2) + F(7))^{F(F(4))}) × F(F(7))) - ((3)!)
- 27474 := (((-(2 - 7))!) × (-4 + F(F(7)))) - (F(4))!
- 27475 := ((2 + F(F(7))) - (((F(4))! - F(F(7))) × (5)!))
- 27476 := (((F(2) + F((F(7) + F(4)))) × (-F(7))) + (F(6))!)
- 27477 := ((2 + 7) × ((4)! - (F(F(7)) × (-F(7))))
- 27478 := (-2) + ((F(F(7)) - 4) × ((F(7) - 8)!))
- 27480 := (((-(2 - 7))!) × (-4 + F(F((8 - 0!))))
- 27482 := (((-2) - (F(F(7)) × (-4)!)) - (F(F(8)) × (-2)))
- 27483 := (((-F(2)) - (F(F(7)) × (-4)!)) - (F(F(8)) × (-F(3))))
- 27484 := (((2 × F(F(7))) × (F(4))! + F(F(8))) × F(F(4)))
- 27486 := ((2 + ((F(F(7)) × (4)! + F(F(8)))) + F(F(F(6))))
- 27487 := (((-2) + F(F(7))) × (-((F(4) - 8))!) - F(F(7)))
- 27488 := (-F(2) + ((-F(7)) × F(((4)! - 8))) + (8)!)
- 27492 := (-2) + (F(F(7)) × (((4 - 9))! - 2))
- 27493 := (-F(2) + (F(F(7)) × (((4 - 9))! - F(3))))
- 27494 := (F((F(2) × F(7))) × ((4)! + (94)))
- 27496 := ((F((2 × 7)) × F((F(4))!)) + ((F(9) × (6)!))
- 27498 := (((F((-2) + F(7))) + ((F(4))!)! × F(9)) - 8)
- 27529 := (F(2) - ((F(F(7)) × (-((5)! - 2))) - F(9)))
- 27544 := (-((F(-((F(2) - F(7)) - (5)))) × F((F(4))!)) + (F((F(4))!)!))
- 27547 := ((F(2) + ((F(F(7)) + (5)! × (F(4))!)) × F(7))
- 27549 := (((-2) × (7)!) + (F((-5) + (4)!)) × 9))
- 27567 := (((-F(2) + F(F(7))) × (5)! - (F(F(6)) × F(7)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 27573 &:= ((F((2+7)) + (5)) \times (-F(7)) + ((3!)!)) \\
 27574 &:= ((-2) \times F(7)) + ((5)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(4))) \\
 27583 &:= ((F((F(2) \times F(7))) \times (5)!) - F((8 + (3)!)) \\
 27584 &:= ((F(2) + (F(F(7)) \times (5)!)) - F((8 + (F(4)!))) \\
 27594 &:= (((2 + F((7 + 5))) \times 9) \times F(F((F(4)!))) \\
 27598 &:= ((-2) - (7)!) - (((5)! \times F(9)) \times (-8)) \\
 27607 &:= (((-F(2)) + F(F(7))) \times ((6 - 0!)!) - F(F(7))) \\
 27612 &:= ((F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (((6 - 1)!) - 2)) \\
 27624 &:= (((F(-(F(2) - F(7)))) \times F(6)) - F(2)) \times (4)! \\
 27626 &:= ((2 \times (7 + (6)!) \times (-2) + F(F(6))) \\
 27632 &:= (((2^{F(7)}) - (6)!) + ((F((3!)!)/2)) \\
 27633 &:= ((-(2^7)) \times F(6)) + F((F(3) + F(F((3)!))) \\
 27635 &:= (((-F(2)) \times F(F(7))) - (-((6)!) \times F((3)!)) \times 5) \\
 27643 &:= (((-2) + F(F(7))) \times (-((6)!) + F(F(4)))/(-3)!) \\
 27645 &:= (((-2) + F(F(7))) + (-((6)!) \times F((F(4)!))) \times (-5)) \\
 27654 &:= ((-2) + F(7)) \times ((F(F(6)) \times (5)!) - (F(4)!)) \\
 27657 &:= ((F(2) + ((7)! \times 6)) - F((5 + F(7)))) \\
 27664 &:= ((-2) \times ((F(7) \times (6)!) - F(6)) + F((4)!)) \\
 27666 &:= (((F(2) + F(F(7))) + ((6)!) \times (F(6) + F(F(6)))) \\
 27674 &:= ((-2) \times ((F(7) \times (6)!) - F(7)) + F((4)!)) \\
 27683 &:= ((2 \times (F(F(7)) - ((6)!)) + F((F(8) + F(3)))) \\
 27694 &:= ((-2) - (7)!) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(9)) \times (-F(4))) \\
 27695 &:= (((2 + F(F(7))) + ((6)!) \times (F(9) - (5))) \\
 27704 &:= -((((-(F(2) - (7)))! + F(F(7))) - F(-(0! - (4)!))) \\
 27715 &:= ((F(2) - F(7)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-1 + (5)!)) \\
 \\
 27720 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 0 \\
 27721 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 1 \\
 27722 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 2 \\
 27723 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 3 \\
 27724 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 4 \\
 27725 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 5 \\
 27726 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 6 \\
 27727 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 7 \\
 27728 &:= (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$27729 := (-2 + F(7)) \times 7!/2 + 9$$

$$27731 := ((-2) + F(7)) \times (((7)!/F(3)) + 1)$$

$$27735 := ((2 + F(7)) + ((F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times (5)!))$$

$$27736 := (((F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (-7)) + (F((3)!))! - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$27738 := (((2 + 7) \times F(F(7))) \times (-3!)) + (8)!)$$

$$27742 := ((-2) + F(7)) \times (((7)! + (4))/2)$$

$$27743 := (((F((F(2) \times F(7))) \times (-7)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) - F(F(F((3)!))))$$

$$27744 := ((F((2 + 7))^{F(7-4)}) \times (4)!)$$

$$27753 := ((2 \times F(7)) + (F(F(7)) \times ((5)! - F(F(3))))$$

$$27758 := -((((2 + 7))! - F(7)) - (5^8))$$

$$27759 := ((-2) - F(F(7))) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-5!)) - F(9))$$

$$27764 := (((-2) + F(7)) \times ((7)! + F(6)))/F(F(4))$$

$$27768 := ((2 \times F(7)) + F(7)) \times ((6)! - 8)$$

$$27784 := ((-(2 - 7) \times (7)! + F((F(8) - F(4))))$$

$$27790 := (((2 \times (7)! + F((F(7) + 9))) - 0!)$$

$$27791 := ((2 \times (7)! + F((F(7) + (9 \times 1))))$$

$$27792 := (((2 \times (7)! + F((F(7) + 9))) + F(2))$$

$$27793 := (((2 \times (7)! + F((F(7) + 9))) + F(3))$$

$$27794 := (((2 \times (7)! + F((F(7) + 9))) + F(4))$$

$$27796 := ((-2) - (7)!) + (F((F(7) - 9)) \times F(F(F(6))))$$

$$27798 := (-((F(2) \times (7)!)) + (F((F(7) - 9)) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$27803 := ((2 - (7)!) + ((F(F(8)) + 0!) \times 3))$$

$$27826 := (2 \times (F(F(7)) + (((F(8) - 2) \times (6)!))))$$

$$27833 := ((2 \times ((7)! + F(8))) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F((3)!))))$$

$$27834 := (((-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times ((8 - 3)!)) - (F(4)!))$$

$$27835 := (((-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times ((8 - 3)!)) - (5))$$

$$27837 := (((F(2) \times F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times 3) - ((7)!)$$

$$27840 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 0$$

$$27841 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 1$$

$$27842 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 2$$

$$27843 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 3$$

$$27844 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 4$$

$$27845 := (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27846 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 6 \\
 27847 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 7 \\
 27848 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 8 \\
 27849 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 - F(4))! + 9 \\
 \\
 27857 &:= ((F(2) + (F(7) \times (-8))) + ((5)! \times F(F(7)))) \\
 27863 &:= ((2 - (7)!) + ((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) \times 3)) \\
 27864 &:= ((2 \times (7)!) + ((F(8) + (6)!) \times (4)!)) \\
 27904 &:= (((-((2^7)) + (9)!)/F((0! + (F(4))!))) \\
 27907 &:= ((F((-2) + F(7))) - (9)!)/(0 - F(7)) \\
 27913 &:= (((2 - F(7)) + (9)!)/13) \\
 27927 &:= ((F(2) \times F(7)) + (((9)! + 2)/F(7))) \\
 27928 &:= ((-2) \times ((7)! + (F(9)^2))) + (8)! \\
 27934 &:= ((F(((2 \times 7) + 9)) - ((3)!)!) - F(4)) \\
 27936 &:= ((F(((2 \times 7) + 9)) - F(F(3))) - ((6)!)) \\
 27937 &:= -(((F(2) - (7)))! - F(((F(9) + F(3)) - F(7)))) \\
 27938 &:= (((F(2) + F((F(7) + 9))) - ((3)!)!) + F(F(8))) \\
 27943 &:= ((F(((2 \times 7) + 9)) + (F(4))!) - ((3)!)!) \\
 27944 &:= ((-2) + (F(F(7)) \times (-9) + (4)!)) \times F((F(4))!) \\
 27945 &:= ((-2) - F(7)) + (F((9 + 4)) \times (5)!) \\
 27946 &:= -((((F(2) - (7)))! - 9) - F((F(F(4)) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 27947 &:= (((-((2 - 7)))! \times F((9 + 4))) - F(7)) \\
 27949 &:= (-2) + ((F(F(7)) \times ((9 - 4)!) - 9)) \\
 27950 &:= ((F(2) - ((7)!/9)) \times (-50)) \\
 27954 &:= ((F(F((-27) + F(9)))) \times (5)!) - (F(4))! \\
 27955 &:= ((-F(2) + (F(F(7)) \times ((9 - 5)!)) \times 5) \\
 27957 &:= (-((27/9)) + ((5)! \times F(F(7)))) \\
 27958 &:= (-2) + (F(F(7)) \times (-((F((9 - 5)) - 8))!)) \\
 27959 &:= (-F(2) - (F(F(7)) \times (((9)! - (5)!) - (9)!)) \\
 \\
 27960 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 0 \\
 27961 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 1 \\
 27962 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 2 \\
 27963 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 3 \\
 27964 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27965 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 5 \\
 27966 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 6 \\
 27967 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 7 \\
 27968 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 8 \\
 27969 &:= (-2 + 7)! \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) + 9 \\
 \\
 27975 &:= (-((F(2) - ((7 + 9)))) + (F(F(7)) \times (5)!)) \\
 27984 &:= (((-((2 - 7)))! \times F((F(9) - F(8)))) + ((4)!)) \\
 27985 &:= (-F(2)) + (((F(7)!/(9!) + F(F(8))) - (5)!)) \\
 27986 &:= (-(((F(2) \times (7)!) - (9)!)/F(8))) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 27988 &:= ((2 - (((7)! - (9)!)/F(8))) + F(F(8))) \\
 28046 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - 0!) - F(-(((F(4))! - F(F(6)))))) \\
 28047 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F(-(((0! - F(4)) - F(7)))))) \\
 28048 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + 0!) - F(-(((F(4))! - (F(8)))))) \\
 28056 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((0! - (5)!) + (6)!)) \\
 28084 &:= (((2^8) + F(-((0! - F(8)))))) \times 4 \\
 28144 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - 1) - (F((F(4))!)^{F(4)})) \\
 28153 &:= (-(((2 + F(8))^{F(-1+5)})) + (F((3)!))!) \\
 28159 &:= ((F(F(-((F(2) - 8)))) \times (1 + (5)!)) - F(9)) \\
 28214 &:= ((-2) - (F(8)^2)) + F((-1 + (4)!)) \\
 28222 &:= (-2) + ((F(8) \times F((F((2 + 2)))!)^2)) \\
 28223 &:= -((F(2) - ((F(8)^2) \times (2^{3!}))) \\
 28249 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((2 \times (F(4))!) \times F(9))) \\
 28274 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) - (F((2 \times 7)))) - (F(4))!) \\
 28280 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - F((2 \times (8 - 0!)))) \\
 28314 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (((3)! + 1)^{F(4)})) \\
 28322 &:= (2 \times (((8 - 3)! - F(2))^2)) \\
 28324 &:= (2 \times (((8)!/3 + 2) + ((F(4))!))!) \\
 28333 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - ((3 \times (3))!)^{F(3)}) \\
 28334 &:= (2 \times (((-((8)!) - F(F((3)!)))/(-3)) + ((F(4))!))!) \\
 28336 &:= (2 \times (((8)!/3 + F((3)!) + ((6)!)) \\
 28344 &:= ((2 \times (((8)!/3 + ((F(4))!))!) + ((4)!)) \\
 28345 &:= (F(2) + (((F(8) \times F((3)!))^{F(F(4))}) + (5)!)) \\
 28347 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(3) - ((4)! \times F(7)))))) \\
 28349 &:= (((F((F(2) + 8))^3) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$28350 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 0$$

$$28351 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 1$$

$$28352 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 2$$

$$28353 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 3$$

$$28354 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 4$$

$$28355 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 5$$

$$28356 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 6$$

$$28357 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 7$$

$$28358 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 8$$

$$28359 := (2 + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) + 9$$

$$28363 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(F((3)!)) \times (F(6) + (3!))))$$

$$28364 := (((F((F(2) + 8))^3) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4)!))$$

$$28365 := (F(-(F(2) - F(8)))) - (((3)! \times (6)! \times (-5)))$$

$$28369 := ((2 \times F(F(8))) - (3 + ((6)! \times (-9))))$$

$$28371 := ((2 \times (F(F(8)) + ((3)!)) + ((7)! - 1))$$

$$28372 := (2 \times ((F(F(8)) + ((3)!)) - ((7)! / (-2))))$$

$$28373 := ((2 \times (F(F(8)) + ((3)!)) - (-((7)! - F(F(3))))$$

$$28374 := (((2 + 8)! / (F(3)^7)) + (4)!)$$

$$28375 := (F((2 + 8)) - ((3 + F(F(7))) \times (-5!)))$$

$$28376 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - F((3)!)) - (F(7) \times F(F(6))))$$

$$28377 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(F((3)!)) \times F(7)) + 7))$$

$$28378 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((3)! + (F(7) \times F(8))))$$

$$28379 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - ((3)!)) + ((F(7) \times F(9))))$$

$$28384 := ((-F((2 \times 8))) + (F((3)!)) - (F(F(8)) + F(4)))$$

$$28385 := (((-2) - F(F(8))) + (F((3)!)) - (F((F(8) - (5))))$$

$$28386 := (((-F(2)) - F(F(8))) - F((F(3) \times 8))) + (F(6)!))$$

$$28388 := (((F(2) + (8)! - F((F(3) \times 8))) - F(F(8)))$$

$$28389 := (F((-2) + F(8))) - (((3)! - 8) \times (-F(9)))$$

$$28392 := 2 \times F(8) \times (F(3!) - F(9))^2$$

$$28393 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F((3)! \times F(9)) - F((3)!)))$$

$$28396 := (((-F((2 \times 8))) + (F((3)!)) + 9) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$28399 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((3)! \times (9 + F(9))))$$

$$28400 := ((-(2^8)) + F((4! - 0!)) - 0!)$$

- 28401 := $(-(2^8) + F((4)! - 0!))$
 28402 := $((-(2^8) + F((4)! - 0!)) + F(2))$
 28403 := $((-(2^8) + F((4)! - 0!)) + F(3))$
 28404 := $((-(2^8) + F((4)! - 0!)) + F(4))$
 28407 := $((F((-2) + F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)) - (0! + (7)!))$
 28408 := $((F((-2) + F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)) - ((0! - 8)!))$
 28413 := $((F(-(F(2) - F(8)))) / (4 + 1) \times F(F((3)!))$
 28415 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (F(F(4)) \times (1 + (5)!))$
 28416 := $((F((2 + F(8))) - F((F(4)!)) - (F(F((1 + 6))))$
 28417 := $((F(2) - 8) + F((4)! - 1)) - F(F(7))$
 28418 := $((F((2 + F(8))) - (F(4)! - F(F(-(1 - 8))))$
 28419 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(4)! + 1) \times F(9))$
 28422 := $((F((2 + F(8))) - F(F((F(4)! + F(2)))) - 2$
 28423 := $((-F(2) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) - F(F((F(2) + (3)!)))$
 28426 := $((2 + ((8 - F(4))!) \times F(F((F(2) + (6))))$
 28430 := $((F((2 + F(8))) + (F(4)! - F(F((3)! + 0!)))$
 28431 := $(F(-(F(2) - 8)) \times (F(4)^{3!+1}))$
 28432 := $((F((2 + F(8))) + F((F(4)!)) - F(F((3)! + F(2))))$
 28433 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (((F(4)!)^3 + F((3)!))$
 28434 := $((2 \times F(8)) \times (-43 + ((F(4)!)!))$
 28435 := $((F(2) + F((F(8) - F(4)))) \times ((3)! + (5))$
 28439 := $(-F(2) + (((8)! \times (4)! - ((3)!!) / F(9)))$
 28440 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (((F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 0!))$
 28441 := $(-((-((2 - 8)^{F(4)})) + F((4)! - 1))$
 28442 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (((F(4)!)^{F(4)} - F(2)))$
 28443 := $((F(2) + F(F(8))) + (((4)! \times (F(4)^{3!})))$
 28444 := $((2 + F(F(8))) + ((F(4)^{F(4)!}) \times (4)!))$
 28445 := $((F(-(F(2) - 8)))^4 - (-4 + (5)!))$
 28447 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (((F(4)! + (4)!) \times 7))$
 28448 := $(-(((F(2) + F(8))^4) - (-((4)! \times F(F(8))))$
 28449 := $((F((2 + F(8))) - 4) - ((F(4)! \times F(9)))$
 28457 := $((((-F(2) + F(F(8))) \times (4)! / (5)! \times F(7))$
 28458 := $((((F(2) - F(F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)) / (-5) + F(F(8)))$
 28459 := $(-F((-2) + F(8))) - (F((F(4)!)) \times (-((5)! \times F(9))))$

- 28463 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((4)! × F(6)) + F(3))
- 28464 := ((-F(2)) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) - (F(6) × (4)!))
- 28465 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((4)! × F(((6)!/(5)!)))
- 28475 := ((-F(2)) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(4))!) × F(7)))/5
- 28477 := (F(2) + ((F(8) × (F(4))!) × (F(F(7)) - 7)))
- 28479 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(F(7)) - F(9)))
- 28480 := (2 × ((-8) + ((F(4))!)!) × (F(8) - 0!))
- 28481 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F((F(4))!) × (F(8) + 1)))
- 28483 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - (F(4))!) + (-F(8) × F((3)!)))
- 28485 := ((F(2) - ((-8) + ((F(4))!)!) × (-8)) × 5)
- 28494 := ((-2) + F(F(8))) + (((F(4) × 9)!/(4)!))
- 28495 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - F((F(4))!)) - (F(9) + (5)!))
- 28496 := (2 × (((F(8) + ((F(4))!)!) × F(9)) - F(F(F(6))))
- 28497 := (((F(2) × F(8)) × F((F((F(4))!) + 9))) - ((7)!))
- 28503 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - (5)! - F((0! + F((3)!))))
- 28508 := (2 × (-F(F(8))) + (5 × (-((0! - 8))!)))
- 28512 := (-2) × ((F(8) - (5)! × F(12)))
- 28514 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! - 1) + (4)!)
- 28516 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - (5)! - F(F((1 × 6))))
- 28524 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - (5)! - F((F(2) + (F(4))!)))
- 28526 := (F((F(2) + 8)) × (((5)! - F(2)) + (6)!))
- 28528 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! + F(2)) + 8)
- 28529 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (((5)! - F(2)) + 9))
- 28530 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! + (3)! + 0!))
- 28532 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! + ((3 + 2))))
- 28533 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! + (3)! - F(3)))
- 28534 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! + (3)! - F(4)))
- 28535 := ((-2) + F((8 + (5 × 3)))) - (5)!)
- 28536 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5)! + ((3)!/6)))
- 28537 := (F((F(2) + F(8))) - (((5)! - F((3 × 7))))
- 28538 := (((F(2)⁸) - (5)! + F((F(3) + F(8))))
- 28539 := (-((F(2) × F(8))) - ((-((5)! - ((3)!!) × F(9))))
- 28540 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 0
- 28541 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 1

$$28542 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 2$$

$$28543 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 3$$

$$28544 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 4$$

$$28545 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 5$$

$$28546 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 6$$

$$28547 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 7$$

$$28548 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 8$$

$$28549 := F(2 + F(8)) - 5! + F(4) + 9$$

$$28552 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (5 \times F(F(((5 - 2)!))))))$$

$$28553 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + (-5 - (5!)) + F(F((3)!)))$$

$$28554 := (((F(F(-(F(2) - 8)))) + (5)) \times (5!) - (F(4)!))$$

$$28555 := (((F(F(-(F(2) - 8)))) + (5)) \times (5!) - (5))$$

$$28558 := ((F((28 - 5)) - (5!)) + F(8))$$

$$28560 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 0$$

$$28561 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 1$$

$$28562 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 2$$

$$28563 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 3$$

$$28564 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 4$$

$$28565 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 5$$

$$28566 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 6$$

$$28567 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 7$$

$$28568 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 8$$

$$28569 := F(F(2) + 8) \times (5! + 6!) + 9$$

$$28579 := ((-2) + F(8)) - (((5!) \times (-7)) \times F(9))$$

$$28586 := (-(((F(2) - 8) \times (5!)) \times F(8))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$28587 := ((F(2) + F(F(8))) - (((5!) \times F(8)) \times (-7)))$$

$$28595 := ((F(2) - 8) \times (-5 - (F(9) \times (5!))))$$

$$28597 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((5!)/(9 - 7)))$$

$$28599 := ((F((2 + F(8))) - (-((5 - 9)!)) - F(9))$$

$$28603 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((F(6) + 0!) \times (3)!))$$

$$28609 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (-6 \times (0! - 9)))$$

$$28612 := ((2 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6)!)/((1 + 2)!))$$

$$28614 := ((-((F(2) + F(8))) - F(F(6))) + F((-1 + (4)!)))$$

$$28620 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6^2) + 0!))$$

$$28630 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 0$$

$$28631 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 1$$

$$28632 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 2$$

$$28633 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 3$$

$$28634 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 4$$

$$28635 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 5$$

$$28636 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 6$$

$$28637 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 7$$

$$28638 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 8$$

$$28639 := F(2 + F(8)) - F(F(6)) - 3! + 9$$

$$28640 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((-6) + (4!) - 0!))$$

$$28645 := ((F(2) - (-8) \times ((6!) - (4))) \times 5)$$

$$28648 := ((-2) - F(F(8))) - (((6!) + (4) - (8)!))$$

$$28650 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(6) - ((5 \times 0)!))$$

$$28651 := (F((2 + F(8))) - ((6)! / ((5 \times 1)!))$$

$$28652 := ((-2) - F(F(8))) + ((6)! \times F((5 \times 2)))$$

$$28653 := ((-F(2) - F(F(8))) - (((6)! - ((5 + 3)!)))$$

$$28656 := (-F(2) + F(((8 \times F(6)) + (5)! / F(6)))$$

$$28660 := (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(6) - (6)) + 0!))$$

$$28661 := (F((-2) + F(8))) - (-((6)! \times F((F(6) + 1))))$$

$$28663 := (F((2 + F(8))) + (((6 - 6) + 3)!))$$

$$28664 := (-((F(2) - 8)) + F((-((6/6) + (4)!)))$$

$$28669 := (F((-2) + F(8))) + ((F(6) + ((6)! \times F(9))))$$

$$28680 := (((2 + F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) + F((F(8) + 0!)))$$

$$28684 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + F(F(6))) + (F((8 - 4)!))$$

$$28685 := ((-2) - ((-8) \times (6)! + F(8))) \times 5$$

$$28688 := ((F((F(2) + 8)) - ((6)! - (8)!)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$28689 := ((F(2) - F(F(8))) - (((6)! - (8)! - F(9))))$$

$$28690 := ((F((F(2) + F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) - 0!))$$

$$28699 := ((F((2 + F(8))) + F((-((6 - 9)!)) + F(9)))$$

$$28704 := ((-(2^8) + (7)! \times (F(04)!))$$

$$28706 := (F((2 + F(8))) + (-7) \times (0! - F(6)))$$

- 28713** := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (7 \times F(((1 \times 3)!)))$
28714 := $((F(2) + ((8 \times 7))) + F((-1 + (4)!))$
28723 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) - 2) \times (3)!))$
28742 := $(-((2 - 87)) + F(((4)! - F(2))))$
28745 := $(-(F((2 + 8))) - ((-(7)!) - ((F(4)!)!) \times 5))$
28747 := $((((-(2) - F(8)) \times (7)!)/(-4)) - F(F(7)))$
28753 := $((F((2 + F(8))) + 7) + F((5 + (3)!))$
28756 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (((F(7) - (5)!) + F(6))))$
28757 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + ((-7) + (5)!) - F(7))$
28758 := $((-(2) \times F(8)) + (((7)! \times (5)!)/F(8)))$
28760 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) \times F(6)) - 0!))$
28765 := $((((F(2) - 8) + (7)!) + (6)!) \times 5)$
28766 := $((((2 - F(F(8))) - F((7 + F(6)))) + (F(6)!)$
28767 := $((((F(28)/F(7)) - (6)!) + (7)!)$
28775 := $((((F((2 + 8)) \times F(7)) + (7)!) \times 5)$
28777 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(7) - F((-7) + F(7))))!)$
28783 := $(F(((2 \times 8) + 7)) + (F(8) \times (3)!))$
28784 := $((F((2 + F(8))) + 7) + ((8 - F(4))!))$
28785 := $((F(((2 \times 8) + 7)) + 8) + (5)!)$
28787 := $((((-(2) \times (8)!)/7) + (8)!) - F(7))$
28793 := $(F(F(-(F(2) - 8))) + (((7)! \times F(9))/(3)!))$
28801 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + F((F((8 - 0!)) - 1)))$
28804 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (-(F(8)) \times (-(0!) - (F(4)!)))$
28805 := $((F(2) - ((8)!/(-8 + 0!))) \times 5)$
28815 := $((F(2) + ((8)!/F(8))) \times 15)$
28816 := $(2 \times (8 + ((F(8) - 1) \times (6)!))$
28824 := $(-((F(2) + (-8) \times F(8))) + F(-((F(2) - (4)!)))$
28825 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (((8)!/2)/(5)!))$
28833 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(8) + F(F(3))) \times F((3)!))$
28835 := $((-((F(2) - 8)) - (-8) \times ((3)!)) \times 5)$
28840 := $((((-(2) + F(8)) + F(8)) \times (((F(4)!)! + 0!))$
28841 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (8 \times ((4)! - 1)))$
28842 := $(2 \times (F(8) + (((8 - F(4))!)^2)))$
28843 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + ((8 \times (4)!) - (3)!))$
28845 := $((((F(2) + 8) - (-8) \times ((F(4)!)!)) \times 5)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28854 &:= (((-2) - (F(F(8)) \times 8))/5) + F((4)!) \\
 28863 &:= ((F(2) - F(F(8))) + (((8)! - (F(6)^3)))) \\
 28864 &:= ((2 - F(F(8))) + (((8)! - (F(6)^{F(4)}))) \\
 28865 &:= (F(2) - (8 \times (-8) - ((6)! \times 5))) \\
 28867 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (((F(8) - (6))!/(F(7))!)) \\
 28868 &:= -((((((2 + F(8))!/(F(8))!) - (F(6))!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 28870 &:= (((F((2 + F(8))) - (F(8))) + F(F(7))) + 0!) \\
 28873 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(8)/7)!^3)) \\
 28874 &:= (((F((2 + F(8))) + 8) + F(F(7))) - ((4)!) \\
 28884 &:= ((F((2 + F(8))) + F((-8) + F(8))) - (F(4))!) \\
 28887 &:= -(((((-((2 - 8)))! + F(F(8))) - (8)! - F(F(7)))) \\
 28890 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + F((F(8) - 9) + 0!)) \\
 28894 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (F(8) - (-9) \times (4)!)) \\
 28895 &:= -(((F(2) - (8)!) + (((8)! \times F(9))/(5)!)) \\
 28896 &:= (((2 \times F(8)) \times (-8)) \times F(9)) + (F(6))! \\
 28904 &:= (((2^8) - 9) + F(-((0! - (4)!))) \\
 28930 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(9) \times F((3)!) + 0!)) \\
 28933 &:= (F((-2) + F(8))) + (F(9) \times (F((3)!) + ((3)!)) \\
 28936 &:= -((F((F(2) + F(8))) + (9 - ((3)!^6))) \\
 28937 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + ((F(9) + (3)!) \times 7)) \\
 28943 &:= (-F((2 + F(8)))) - (((9)!/F(F((F(4))!))) - (F((3)!))!) \\
 28944 &:= (((-((F(2) - 8)))! - (9 \times (4)!) \times (F(4))! \\
 28947 &:= (F((2 \times 8)) + (((9 - 4)! \times F(F(7)))) \\
 29034 &:= (F((2 + F((9 - 0!)))) + F((F((3)!) + (F(4)!))) \\
 29074 &:= (((2^9) + 0!) + (F(7)^4)) \\
 29084 &:= ((-290) - F(F(8))) + (F((F(4))!))! \\
 29088 &:= ((-2) - ((9)!/(0! - F(8))) + F(F(8))) \\
 29144 &:= -((((F(F(-(2 - 9))) - (F((-1 + (4)!))) - ((F(4))!))!)) \\
 29148 &:= (((2^9) + F((-1 + (4)!)) - (F(8))) \\
 29238 &:= ((((-2) \times F(9)) \times 2) + (F((3)!))! - F(F(8))) \\
 29242 &:= (F(2) + ((9 \times (-2) + F(F((F(4))!)))^2)) \\
 29243 &:= (2 + ((9 \times (-2) + F(F((F(4))!)))^{F(3)})) \\
 29246 &:= (((-((2^9-2)) + (F((F(4))!))! - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 29253 &:= (((-F(2)) - F(F((9 - F(2)))) - (5)!) + (F((3)!))!
 \end{aligned}$$

- 29254 := (((-F(2)) × F(F((9 - F(2)))))) - (5)!) + (F((F(4))!))!
- 29256 := ((2 - F(F((9 - F(2)))))) - ((5)! - (F(6))!))
- 29260 := (-((2 - 9)) × (F((-2) + F(F(6)))) - 0!)
- 29273 := ((F(F(2) + ((9 × 2)))) × 7) + (3)!
- 29274 := (-((2 - 9)) × (F(2) + F((F(7) + (F(4))!))))
- 29283 := (((F(2) - (92)) - F(F(8))) + (F((3))!))!
- 29284 := (((2 - 92) - F(F(8))) + (F((F(4))!))!)
- 29286 := (((F(2) - F((9 + 2))) - F(F(8))) + (F(6))!)
- 29304 := (((2 × F((9 + (3)!))) + 0!) × (4)!)
- 29306 := (((-2) × F(9)) + (F((3))!))! - F(F(F(06)))
- 29318 := ((-F((F(2) + 9))) + (F((3))!))! + (-1 - F(F(8)))
- 29319 := ((-F((F(2) + 9))) + (F((3))!))! - F(F(-(1 - 9)))
- 29323 := (-((2 - 9)) × (F((3)!) + F((-2) + F(F((3)!)))))
- 29332 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! - F(F(F((3)!)))) - (F(F((3)!) × 2))
- 29333 := ((-((F(2) + F(9))) - F(F(F((3)!)))) - ((3)! - (F((3)!))!))
- 29334 := (((F(F(-(2 - 9)))) × (3)!) × F(F((3)!)) - ((4)!))
- 29335 := ((-((F(2) × F(9))) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + (((F((3))!)! - (5))))
- 29336 := (((2 - F(9)) + (F((3)!))! - (3)!) - F(F(F(6))))
- 29337 := (F(-(F(2) - 9)) × (-F(F(3)) + (-((3)!) × F(F(7))))
- 29338 := (((-2) - F(9)) + (F((3 + 3))!)) - F(F(8))
- 29339 := (((-F(2)) - F(F(F((9 - 3)))))) + (F((3))!))! - F(9)
- 29340 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! - F(F(F((3)!)))) - F((F((F(4))!) + 0!)))
- 29341 := (((-2) - F(9)) + ((3)!)!) + F(((4)! - 1))
- 29342 := ((-((F(2) + F(9))) + ((3)!)!) + F(((4)! - F(2))))
- 29343 := ((29 × F((F(3)⁴))) + ((3)!)!)
- 29344 := (((F(2) - F(9)) + ((3)!)!) + F(((4)! - F(F(F(4)))))
- 29345 := ((-29) + (F((3)!)!)) - F(F((F(4) + (5))))
- 29346 := (((F(F(-(2 - 9))) × F(F((3)!)) - F(F(4))) × 6
- 29347 := (-((2 + 9)) - (F(F((3)!) × (-((F(4))! × F(F(7)))))
- 29348 := (((-2) + (F((9 - 3))!)) - ((4)!) - F(F(8))
- 29349 := (((F(F(-(2 - 9))) × F(F((3)!)) × (F(4))!) - 9
- 29350 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! - F(F(F((3)!)))) - ((5 - 0)!)!
- 29353 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! - F(F((3)!)) - F(F((5 + 3))))
- 29354 := ((F(F(-(2 - 9))) × ((3)! + (5)!)) - 4
- 29356 := ((-((2 × 9)) - F(F((3 + 5)))) + (F(6))!)

$$\begin{aligned} 29357 &:= (-F(2)) + (((9 - 3) + (5)!) \times F(F(7))) \\ 29358 &:= (F(-(F(2) - 9))) \times ((3)! \times F((5 + 8))) \\ 29360 &:= (((-F(-(2 - 9)))) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(F(6))) - 0! \\ 29361 &:= ((-F(-(2 - 9))) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(F((6 \times 1)))) \\ 29362 &:= (((-F(-(2 - 9)))) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(F(6))) + F(2) \\ 29363 &:= ((-(2 + 9)) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F((6 + F(3)))) \\ 29364 &:= ((-2) - (-F(9) \times F((F(3) \times 6)))) \times (F(4))! \\ 29365 &:= (-((F(2) + F(9))) \times (F(F(3)) - (((6)! + (5)!))) \\ 29366 &:= ((-F((2 \times 9) + 3)) + (F(6))!) - F(6) \\ 29367 &:= ((-F((2 \times 9) + 3)) + (F(6))!) - 7 \\ 29368 &:= -(((F((2 \times 9) + 3)) + (6)) - (8)!) \\ 29369 &:= (((29 + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(9)) \\ 29371 &:= ((-((F(2) - 9)))! - (3 + F(F((7 + 1)))) \\ 29372 &:= ((-((F(2) - 9)))! - (F((3 \times 7)) + 2)) \\ 29373 &:= ((-F(2) + (F((9 - 3)))!) - F((7 \times 3))) \\ 29374 &:= (((F((2 + 9))^3) + (7)) / (4)!) \\ 29375 &:= -((F(2) - ((F(9) \times (3)!) \times F((7 + 5)))) \\ 29376 &:= ((F((2 \times (9 - 3))) - (7)!) \times (-6)) \\ 29377 &:= (F((29 - (3)!)) - ((7)! / (-7))) \\ 29378 &:= ((-((F(2) - 9)))! - ((3 - 7) + F(F(8)))) \\ \\ 29380 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 0 \\ 29381 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 1 \\ 29382 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 2 \\ 29383 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 3 \\ 29384 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 4 \\ 29385 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 5 \\ 29386 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 6 \\ 29387 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 7 \\ 29388 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 8 \\ 29389 &:= (-F(2) + 9)! + 3! - F(F(8)) + 9 \\ \\ 29392 &:= (((2 \times 9) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F((9 - F(2)))) \\ 29393 &:= (((F(2) + 9) - F(F(F((3)!)))) - (-9 - (F((3)!))!) \\ 29394 &:= (((2 + 9) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + 9) + (F((F(4)!))! \end{aligned}$$

- 29395 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! - F(F(F((3)!)))) + F(F((F((9 - 5))))!))
- 29396 := (((F(-(2 - 9))) + (F((3)!))!) + 9) - F(F(F(6)))
- 29398 := ((-((F(2) + 9)) + (F((3)!))!) - (-F(9) + F(F(8))))
- 29399 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! - F(F(F((3)!)))) + (F(9) - 9))
- 29403 := ((29 + (F((F(4)!))!) - F(F(F((03)!))))
- 29404 := ((29 - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (0! + (F((F(4)!))!))
- 29406 := ((29 + F((4)! - 0!)) + ((6)!))
- 29407 := ((-((F(2) - F(9))) + (F((F(4)!))!) - (F(F((0! + (7))))))
- 29408 := ((-((F(2) - F(9))) + (F((F(4)!))!) + (0! - F(F(8))))
- 29409 := (((F(2) + F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - F(F(-(0! - 9))))
- 29413 := (((2 + F(9)) + F((4)! - 1)) + ((3)!))
- 29424 := (((F(2) + F(9))^{F(F(4))}) + F(2)) × (4)!)
- 29427 := (((29^{F(4)}) - 2) + (7)!)
- 29428 := ((F((F(2) + 9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - (F(2) + F(F(8))))
- 29429 := ((29^{F(4)}) + (-((2 - 9)))!)
- 29430 := (((F((F(2) + 9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + 0!)
- 29432 := ((F((F(2) + 9)) + ((F(4)!))!) + F((F(F((3)!)) + 2)))
- 29433 := (((F(2) + F(9)) + (4)! + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(F((3)!))))
- 29434 := (((2 × F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - F(F(F((3)!)))) - F((F(4)!))
- 29436 := (((2 × (F(9) - F(4))) + (F((3)!))!) - F(F(F(6))))
- 29437 := (((29^{F(4)}) + F((3)!)) + ((7)!))
- 29438 := ((-((F(2) - 9)))! + ((4³) - F(F(8))))
- 29441 := (((2 × F(9)) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (((F((F(4)!))!) - 1)))
- 29442 := (((2 × F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - F(F((4 × 2))))
- 29443 := ((F(2) + ((F(9) × 4)^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F((3)!))))
- 29444 := ((2 × F(9)) × ((F(F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))}) - F((F(4)!))
- 29446 := (((-((F(2) - 9)))! + ((4)! × F(4))) - F(F(F(6))))
- 29447 := (F((2 + 9)) - (F(F((F(4)!)) × (-((F(4)! × F(F(7))))))
- 29448 := ((F((2 × 9)) × ((4)! + F(4))) - (8)!)
- 29458 := ((F((2 + 9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - (5 + F(F(8))))
- 29460 := (((2⁹) - F(F((F(4)!))))) × 60
- 29462 := ((F((2 + 9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) - (F(F(F(6))) + F(2)))
- 29463 := ((-((2 + 9)) × F(((4)! - F(6)))) + (F((3)!))!)
- 29464 := (F((2 × 9)) + ((4 × (F(6)!)) / (F(4)!))

$$29465 := ((-(29) + (F((F(4))!))!) - (F(F(F(6))) - (5)!))$$

$$29468 := (((F(2) \times 94) + (F(6))!) - F(F(8)))$$

$$29470 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 0$$

$$29471 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 1$$

$$29472 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 2$$

$$29473 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 3$$

$$29474 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 4$$

$$29475 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 5$$

$$29476 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 6$$

$$29477 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 7$$

$$29478 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 8$$

$$29479 := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))/F(7) + 9$$

$$29484 := (((F(2) + F((9 + 4))) \times F(8)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$29485 := (((F(2) \times (-9)) + (F((F(4))!))!) - (F(F(8)) - (5)!))$$

$$29486 := (2 \times (((9)!/(4)!) - F((8 + 6))))$$

$$29494 := -(((F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) - (F((F(4))!))!) - ((9 - 4)!))$$

$$29496 := ((-((2 - 9)))! - ((4)! - (F(9) \times (6)!)))$$

$$29499 := (F(2) + ((-F(9)) + ((F(4))!)) \times (9 + F(9)))$$

$$29514 := (((-((2 - 9)))! - ((5)! + 1)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$29526 := (((-((2 - 9)))! - ((5)! - F(2))) \times 6)$$

$$29533 := (((F(2) + (9^5))/F(3)) + F((3)!))$$

$$29534 := (((2 - (9^5)) - F(F((3)!)))/(-F(F(4))))$$

$$29543 := ((-((F(2) + (F(9) \times (-5)))) + (F((F(4))!))!) - F(F(F((3)!))))$$

$$29544 := (((-((2 - 9)))! - ((5)! - (4))) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$29547 := (((F(2) + F(9)) \times (5)!) + F(F((F(4))!))) \times 7$$

$$29554 := (2 \times (F((9 + 5)) + ((5)!^{F(F(4))})))$$

$$29561 := (((2 + F(9)) + (5)) \times ((6)! + 1))$$

$$29564 := (((2 \times 95) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(4))!))!)$$

$$29568 := ((2 + 9) \times (((5)! + F(6)) \times F(8)))$$

$$29573 := -((F(2) + (((-9) + (5)!) - (7)!) \times (3)!))$$

$$29574 := (2 \times (((9 - (5)!) + (7)!) \times F(4)))$$

$$29575 := ((F(2) + F(9)) \times (((5)! \times 7) + (5)))$$

$$29583 := (((F((2 + 9)) + (5)!) - F(F(8))) + (F((3)!))!)$$

- 29606 := ((F(F(-(2-9)))) - F(F(F(6)))) - (0! - (F(6)!))
29607 := (((-(F(2)-9))!) - F(F(F(6)))) - (0 - F(F(7)))
29608 := (F(F(-(2-9))) + (((F(6)! + 0!) - F(F(8))))
29635 := (((-(-(2-9)))! + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F((3)!))) × 5
29638 := (-2) + ((F(9) + (6)) × (((3)! + (F(8))))
29640 := (F(-(F(2)-9)) + ((6)!)) × 40
29643 := (((F(2) + F(9)) + (6)) × (F(4) + ((3)!))
29646 := (((-(-(2-9)))! + F(F(6))) × (F(4)!)) - ((6)!))
29647 := (((-(F(2)-9))!) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F((F(4)!)) × F(7)))
29648 := (((2 + (F(9) × F(6))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) - F(F(8)))
29664 := (2 × ((F((9+6)) + F(6)) × (4)!))
29666 := (((2 × 9) + F(6)) × (6)! + F(F(F(6))))
29667 := (((2 × (9)!)/F(F(6))) - (F(F(6)) × F(F(7))))
29668 := ((2 + ((F(9) - F(6)) × (6)!)) + F(F(8)))
29675 := (((29 + F(F(F(6)))) - ((7)!)) × 5
29694 := (-((F(-(2-9)) - ((6)!)) × (F(9) + F((F(4)!))))
29706 := (F((2+9)) - (7)! × (0-6))
29734 := ((-(2⁹)) + ((7)! × (3)!)) + (F(4)!))
29735 := (-F((2+9))) + (F(F(7)) × (F((3)! + (5)!))
29736 := (((2 + F(9)) + (7)! × (3)! - (6)!))
29746 := (-((2⁹)) - (((7)! + F(4)) × (-6)))
29753 := (F(F(-(2-9))) + (((7)! - (5)! × (3)!))
29756 := ((-2) × F(9)) + (F(F(7)) × ((5)! + F(6)))
29764 := (-((2⁹)) - (-((7)! + (6)) × (F(4)!))
29766 := (((F(2) × F(9)) + (7)) × ((6)! + (6)))
29774 := ((-(F(2)-9))!) - ((F(F(7)) + ((7)!)) × F(F(4)))
29778 := (((2 + (9)!)/F(7)) - (F(F(7)) × (-8)))
29784 := (((-2) × F(9)) + (7)! - 8) × (F(4)!))
29824 := ((2 × F((F(9) - F(8)))) × (2^{F(4)!)})
29836 := (2 × (-F(9)) - ((8 - ((3)!)) × F(F(6))))
29846 := (((F(2) + 9)!/(8 × (4)!)) + F(F(F(6))))
29848 := (-(((F(2) - F(9)) - 8) × (((F(4)!))! + 8))
29854 := ((-(F(2)-9))!) - (F(F(8)) + ((5)! × (-4)))
29856 := (((((F(2) + 9)! + (8)!)/(5)! - ((6)!))
29857 := (-((F(2) - F(9))) + ((8 + (5)! × F(F(7))))

$$\begin{aligned} 29873 &:= (((2^9) - F(F(8))) - F(7)) + (F((3)!))! \\ 29883 &:= (((2^9) - F(F(8))) + (((8)! - 3))) \\ 29884 &:= (((2^9) - F(F(8))) + (8)!) - F(F(4)) \\ 29886 &:= (2 \times (-9) + (F(8) \times (-8) + (6)!)) \\ 29934 &:= (((-(2-9))! / 9) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + (F((F(4))!))! \\ 29944 &:= (F((2 \times 9)) - (-((F(9) + 4))) \times ((F(4))!)) \\ 29946 &:= ((-2) + (F(9) \times (F(9) + F((F(4))!)))) \times F(F(6)) \\ 29948 &:= (((F((2 \times 9)) + 9) \times (-4)) + (8)!) \\ 29956 &:= ((F(29) - (9)!) - F((5 + F(F(6)))) \\ 29968 &:= (((F((2 + 9)) \times F(9)) + (6)!) \times 8) \\ 29969 &:= ((-((F(2) - 9)))! - (((9)! - F(F(F(6)))) / F(9))) \\ 29973 &:= -((F(F(-(2-9)))) + (F(9) - ((7)! \times (3)!))) \\ 29976 &:= (((F(2) + 9) + F(9)) - (7)!) \times (-6) \\ 29986 &:= (((2 \times 9) \times F(9)) - F(F(8))) + (F(6))! \\ 30036 &:= ((F((F((3)!) + 0!)) - ((0! + (3)!))!) \times (-6)) \\ 30057 &:= (((3^{0!+0!}) + (5)!) \times F(F(7))) \\ 30093 &:= (((((3)!)! - 0!) + (-((0! - 9)))!) - F(F(F((3)!)))) \\ 30094 &:= (((F((3)!)! - F(F(((0 - 0!) + 9)))) + ((F(4))!))! \\ 30135 &:= (F(F((3)!)) \times (((0! + 1) \times ((3)!))! - (5))) \\ 30176 &:= -(((F((3)!)^{0!+1}) - ((7)! \times 6))) \\ 30186 &:= (((F((3)!) + 0!) - (-((1 - 8)))!) \times (-6)) \\ 30198 &:= (((3)!)! - 0!) \times (F((1 \times 9)) + 8) \\ 30204 &:= (((((3)!) + 0!)! - ((2 + 0!)!)) \times (F(4))! \\ 30225 &:= ((F((F(F((3)!) - 0!)) - ((F((2 + 2)))!))!)) \times 5) \\ 30227 &:= (((((3)!) + 0!)! \times (F((2 + 2)))!) - F(7)) \\ 30232 &:= ((((((3)!) + 0!)! - F(2)) \times (3)!) - 2) \\ 30233 &:= ((((((3)!) + 0!)! - F(2)) \times (3)!) - F(F(3))) \\ 30234 &:= ((3)! \times ((0 - F(2)) + ((3 + 4))!)) \\ 30236 &:= ((((((3)!) + 0!)! - 2) \times (3)!) + F(6)) \\ 30238 &:= -((F(3) \times (0! - (((2 \times 3)!) \times F(8)))) \\ 30239 &:= (-F(F(3))) + (((0! + 2)!) \times (-((F(3) - 9)))!) \\ 30244 &:= ((((((3)!) + 0!)! + F(2)) \times (F(4))! - F(F(4))) \\ 30246 &:= ((3)! \times (0! + (((2 \times 4)!) / F(6)))) \\ 30253 &:= (F(((3)!) + 0!)) + (((2 + 5)!) \times (3)!) \\ 30254 &:= (F((3)!) - (-((0! + ((2 + 5)!)!)) \times (F(4))!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 30260** := $((F(F((3)!)) \times (0! + (2 \times (6)!))) - 0!$
30261 := $(F(F((3)!)) - (((0! + 2)! \times (-((6 + 1)!))))$
30262 := $((F(F((3)!)) \times (0! + (2 \times (6)!))) + F(2))$
30263 := $((F(F((3)!)) \times (0! + (2 \times (6)!))) + F(3))$
30274 := $(-F(3) + (((0! + 2)! + ((7)!)) \times (F(4)!))$
30279 := $((3)! \times (F(((0! + 2)! + ((7)!))) - 9)$
30281 := $(((((3)! + 0!) \times (2 \times F(8))) - 1)$
30282 := $(((((3)! + 0!) \times ((F(2) \times F(8)) \times 2))$
30283 := $(((((3)! + 0!) \times (2 \times F(8))) + F(F(3)))$
30284 := $(((((3)! + 0!) \times (2 \times F(8))) + F(F(4)))$
30287 := $-((F(F(3)) + (((0! + 2)! \times (-8 - (7)!))))$
30294 := $((F((3)! + 0!) + (-((2 - 9)!)) \times (F(4)!))$
30303 := $(F(F((3)!)) \times (0! - (((3)! + 0!) \times (-F(3))))$
30318 := $((3)! \times (F((0! + (3)!)) + (-((1 - 8)!))$
30324 := $((3)! + 0!) \times (((3)! + 2) \times (F(4)!))$
30326 := $(F(3) \times (0! + (((3)! + 2) \times F(F(6))))$
30329 := $((3)! \times ((0! + (3)!)) + (F((2 + 9)))$
30334 := $(((((3)! - 0!)! \times F((3)!)) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + (F((F(4)!))!))$
30335 := $(((((F((3)!))! + 0!) - F(F(F((3)!)))) - (F((3)! \times (-5)!))$
30336 := $((F((3)! + ((0! + (3)!))! + F((3)!)) \times 6)$
30338 := $(-(((3)! + 0!)) - ((F(F((3)!))³) - (8)!))$
30343 := $(F(((F((3)! + 0!) + F((3)!)) \times (-F(F(4))) + F(F((3)!))))$
30344 := $((F(F(F((3)!)) \times (0! + 3)) - ((F((F(4)!))!)/F(4)))$
30345 := $(F(F((3)!)) \times (((03)! \times F(F(4))) + (5)))$
30347 := $(((((3)! + 0!)! - F(F((3)!)) \times (F(4)!)) + F(F(7)))$
30348 := $(F(3) \times ((-0!) + F((F(3) + (4)!)))/8)$
30354 := $(((((3)! \times ((0! + (3)!))! + (5)! - (F(4)!))$
30362 := $(((((F((3)!))! + 0!) - F(F(F((3)!)))) + (F((F(6) \times 2))))$
30363 := $(-3 - (((0! + (3)!))! + F(F(6))) \times (-3!))$
30364 := $(-F(3) + (((0! + (3)!))! + F(F(6))) \times (F(4)!))$
30367 := $(F(F(3)) - ((0 - (3)! \times (F(F(6)) + ((7)!))))$
30368 := $(F(3) \times (0! + ((3 + (6)! \times F(8))))$
30371 := $((3)! \times ((0! + F(F((3)!)) + ((7)!)) - 1)$
30373 := $(F(F(3)) - (((0! + F(F((3)!)) + ((7)!)) \times (-3!))$
30374 := $((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) \times (-(((3)! + 7))) + F((4)!))$

- 30376** := (((3)! × ((0! + 3)!) + ((7)!)) - F(6))
30378 := ((3)! × ((F(03) + (7)!) + F(8)))
30382 := -((((3)! + 0!)! - (F(3) × F((F(8) + F(2))))))
30384 := (((3)! × ((0! + (3)!))!) + F((8 + 4)))
30386 := (((F((3)!))! / F(03)) + ((F(F(8)) - ((6)!)))
30387 := (((3)! × ((0! + (3)!))!) + (F(8) × 7))
30395 := ((F((F(F((3)!)) - 0!)) - ((3)! - F(9))) × 5)
30396 := ((((((3)! + 0!)! - F((3)!)) + F(9)) × 6)
30397 := (F(F(F((3)!))) - (-((0! + (3⁹))) + F(F(7))))
30429 := (F(F((3)!)) × (F((04)! / (-2 + F(9))))
30432 := ((((((3)! × (-0!)) + F((4)!)) / 3) × 2)
30434 := (F(3) × (0! - ((F((4)! - ((3)!)) / (-F(4))))
30437 := ((((((3)! + 0!)! - (F(4)!)) × (3)! + F(F(7)))
30444 := ((((((3)! + 0!)! + F((F(4) × F(4)))) × (F(4)!))
30453 := (F((F(F((3)!)) - 0!)) - (-((4)! × F((-5 + F(F((3)!))))))
30454 := -(((F(F(F((3)!))) + ((0! + F((F(4)!)) × (-5)!)) - (F((F(4)!))!))
30456 := (((3)!^{F(04)}) × ((5)! + F(F(6))))
30457 := ((F(F((3)! + 0!)) - 4) × ((5)! + F(7)))
30464 := ((-((F((3)!))!) × F((0! + F((F(4)!)))) / (-F(F(6)) + ((4)!)))
30467 := ((((((3)! + 0!)! × (F(4)!)) - 6) + F(F(7)))
30472 := ((((((3)! + 0!)! × (F(4)!)) + F(F(7))) - F(2))
30473 := (F(F((3 + 04))) + ((7)! × (3)!))
30474 := ((((((3)! + 0!)! + ((F(4) × F(7)))) × (F(4)!))
30475 := (-(((3)! - 0!)) - ((F(F((F(4)!)) + F(F(7))) × (-5)!))
30476 := (F(F(((3)! + 0!))) + ((F(4) + ((7)! × 6)))
30477 := ((3 + 0!) - (((F(4)! × (-7)!)) - F(F(7))))
30478 := (-F(3) + (((0! + (4)!))! × (F(F(7)) + (F(8))))
30480 := (((((3)! - 0!)! × (F(F((F(4)!)) + (F(F((8 - 0!))))))
30487 := ((((((3)! - 0!)! × (F(F(4))⁸)) - F(F(7)))
30494 := -((((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) × ((F(4)!))! - (-F(9) + F((4)!))))
30524 := -(((F((3)!))! + ((0! - 5) × F((-2 + (4)!))))
30537 := ((3^{-0!+5}) × F((F(3) × 7)))
30544 := ((F(F((3)! + 0!)) × (5)! + F((F(4) × (F(4)!)))
30546 := (((F(F((3)!)) - (0! - 5)!))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6))))

- 30576** := $((F((3)!) + ((0! + (5))))!) \times (7 \times 6)$
30594 := $(((((3)! + 0!))! + 59) \times (F(4))!)$
30599 := $((F((3)!)! - (0! - ((5)! \times (-9 \times 9)))))$
30617 := $((3)! \times ((0! + (6)))! + F((1 + F(7))))$
30624 := $(((((3)! + 0!))! + ((F(6)^2))) \times (F(4))!)$
30628 := $((3^{0!+F(6)} - F(2)) + F(F(8)))$
30629 := $(F(F(F((3)!))) - (0 - ((6/2)^9)))$
30630 := $((3^{0!+F(6)} + F(F(F((3)!)))) + 0!)$
30644 := $-((F((F((3)! + 0!)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4))!)! \times (-F(4))))))$
30647 := $((F((3)!)! - (0! + (((6)! + (4)!) \times F(7))))$
30648 := $((F(((3)! + 0!)) \times (-((6)! + (4)!))) + (8)!)$
30649 := $((F(F((3)!)) - 0!) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4)^9)$
30656 := $((F(30) \times 6) / (5)!) - F(F(F(6)))$
30663 := $(((-(((3)! - 0!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((6)!) \times 3)$
30669 := $((3 \times ((0 - (6)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 9)$
30674 := $(((((3)!)! + 0!) + F(F(6))) \times (-F(7))) + (F((F(4))!)!))$
30675 := $(3 \times (-((0! + (6)!) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))))))$
30677 := $((3)! \times (F((0! + F(6))) + ((7)!)) + F(F(7)))$
30678 := $(3 \times ((0 - (6)!) + F((F(7) + 8))))$
30680 := $((3 \times ((0! - (6)!) + F(F(8)))) - 0!)$
30681 := $(3 \times ((0! - (6)!) + F(F((8 \times 1))))))$
30682 := $((3 \times ((0! - (6)!) + F(F(8)))) + F(2))$
30683 := $(F(3) - ((-((0! - (6)!) - F(F(8))) \times 3))$
30684 := $((F(3) - (06)!) + F(F(8))) \times F(4)$
30686 := $((3 \times ((0 - (6)!) + F(F(8)))) + F(6))$
30687 := $((F((3)!)! - (((06)! + F(8)) \times F(7)))$
30693 := $(3 \times ((-0!) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(9) \times F(F((3)!))))$
30734 := $((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) \times ((F(F(7)) \times (3)!) - F(F(F(4)))))$
30738 := $((-((3)!) \times F(((0! + F(7)) + 3))) + (8)!)$
30743 := $(F(((3 + 0!))!) - ((7 - F(F(4)))^{3!}))$
30744 := $((3 \times (07)!) + F((4)!)) / F(F(4))$
30745 := $((30 + F(7)) \times (((F(4))!)! - (5)))$
30746 := $((-(((3)!)! - ((0! + (7))!) / F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
30748 := $((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) \times (F(4))!) - 8)$

$$30756 := ((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) \times ((-5) + F(6))))!$$

$$30757 := (F(F(3)) - (((0! - F(7)) - (5)!) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$30762 := ((3)! \times (0! + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(2))))$$

$$30764 := (((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) \times 6)) + F((F(4)!)))$$

$$30766 := (((3)! \times (-0! + F(F(7)))) + (F(6)!) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$30767 := ((F((3)!))! - (-((0! - (7 \times 6))) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$30774 := ((3)! \times ((07)! + F((7 + 4))))$$

$$30778 := (((((3)!!) + (0! + F(7))) \times (-F(7))) + (8)!)$$

$$30786 := (((3)!!) + F(07)) \times (F(8) + F(F(6)))$$

$$30834 := ((((((3)! + 0!)!) - F(8)) \times (3)!) + ((F(4)!))!)$$

$$30843 := ((F((3)!))! - (F(-((0! - 8))) \times (F(4)^3)))$$

$$30844 := (-F(3)) \times (F((0! + 8)) - (F((4)!)/F(4)))$$

$$30864 := ((F((-3) + F(08))) \times (-6)) + F((4)!)$$

$$30870 := (F(F((3)!)) \times ((0 - F(8)) \times (-70)))$$

$$30885 := (-3) - ((F(-((0! - 8))))!/(8)! \times (-5)))$$

$$30906 := (((F((3 + 0!)!))!)/(-9) + 0!) \times (-6)$$

$$30912 := ((F(((3 + 0!)!))!)/(-9) \times (-((1 + 2)!))$$

$$30924 := (((F((3 + 0!)!))!)/9 + 2) \times (F(4)!)$$

$$30932 := ((F(F((3)!)) + 0!) \times (-F(9)) - (((3)!!) \times (-2)))$$

$$30933 := (F(F((3)!)) \times ((-((0! - F(9))) + ((3)!!) + ((3)!!))$$

$$30939 := (F((F(F((3)!)) - 0!)) - ((-9) + ((3)!!) \times (-F(9))))$$

$$30946 := ((F(3) \times ((0! + 9)^4)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$30947 := ((F((3)!))! - ((0! + ((9 - F(4))))! \times F(7)))$$

$$30954 := (((3)!!) - (((0! + 9)!)/(-5)!) + (F(4)!))$$

$$30960 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 0$$

$$30961 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 1$$

$$30962 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 2$$

$$30963 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 3$$

$$30964 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 4$$

$$30965 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 5$$

$$30966 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 6$$

$$30967 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 7$$

$$30968 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 8$$

$$30969 := 3!! \times (0! + F(9) + F(6)) + 9$$

- 30973** := (((((3)!)! - ((0 × 9)!) × (-F(7))) + (F((3)!)!))
30974 := (F(F(F((3)!))) + ((0! - F(9)) + (7)!) × 4))
30975 := (((F(F((3)!)) × (-F((0! + 9)))) - ((7)!) × (-5))
30978 := (((F((3)!) + 0!) × F(9)) × F(F(7))) - (8)!)
30979 := -(((F((3)!)! - (0! - ((-F(9)) × F(F(7))) × 9))))
30984 := (((3)!)! × ((0! + F(9)) + 8)) + ((4)!)
30987 := ((F((3)!) + 0!) × (-F((9 + 8)) - (7)!))
30994 := (F((F((3)!) + 0!)) - ((-9) - F(9)) × ((F(4)!)!))
30996 := (F(3) × ((0! - F((9 + 9))) × (-6)))
31106 := (((F((3)!)!)/(1 + 1)) + F(F(F(06))))
31149 := ((F((F((3)!) + 11)) - ((F(4)!)!) × 9)
31238 := (((F((F(F((3)!)) - 1)) - F(2)) × 3) + F(F(8)))
31241 := (F((3 × ((1 + 2)!)!)) + F(((4)! - 1)))
31244 := ((-(((3)!)! × F(F(((1 + 2)!)!))) - (4 - F((4)!)))
31246 := ((F(((3 + 1)!)! - 2) - (((F(4)!)! × F(F(6))))
31247 := (F(((3 + 1)!)! - (F(2) + (F(4) × (7)!)))
31248 := (((31 × 2) × (4)!) × F(8))
31249 := -((F((F(F((3)!)) + 1)) + ((-2) × ((F(4)!)!) × F(9))))
31254 := (F(3) × ((1 × 2) + (5^{F(4)!})))
31339 := (((3)! + 1) × (-3 - ((F((3)!)!)/(-9))))
31349 := (F(F(F((3)!))) + (((1 × 3)!)! + ((F(4)⁹)))
31353 := (F(((3 + 1)!)! + (F(F((3)!) × (5 - ((3)!)!)))
31360 := (((F((3)!)!)/(-1 - F((3)!))) × (-6 - 0!))
31372 := ((F(F((3)!)) + 1) × (((3)!)! - 7) × 2))
31374 := (((F(F((3)!)) × (1 + F((3)!))) + ((7)!) × (F(4)!)
31395 := (((3)! + 1) × (((F((3)!)!)/9) + (5)))
31437 := ((F((3)!)! - ((1 + F((F(4)!)!)) × F((3 + F(7))))))
31447 := (((3)!)! × (1 × 44)) - F(F(7))
31449 := ((F(F(((3)! + 1))) + ((F(4)!)!) × ((4)! + 9))
31455 := (F(F(((3)! + 1))) × ((F(4) × 5) + (5)!))
31464 := ((F((3)!)! - ((F(14) - F(6)) × (4)!))
31474 := (((F((F(F((3)!)) - 1)) × F(4)) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))
31476 := (((F(F(3!)) + 1) × ((F(4)!)! × F(F(7)))) + (6!))
31483 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(14) + (8!/F(3))))

- 31484** := $((F(3!))! - ((1 + (F(4!)/F(8))) \times 4))$
31488 := $((((3 + 1) \times F(4!))/(-F(8))) + 8!)$
31500 := $(F(F(3!)) \times 1500)$
31534 := $((F(3!))! - F(F(F((1 + 5)))) + (3!! \times F(4)))$
31536 := $((3!^{1+5}) - (3!! \times F(F(6))))$
31550 := $((F(F(3!)) + (F(15))) \times 50)$
31563 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - 1)/5 - ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3!))!))$
31584 := $((3 - 1)^5 \times F((-8) + 4!))$
31593 := $((3!! + 1) \times 59 - F(F(F(3!))))$
31618 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - ((-1) \times F(6)) \times F(18))$
31636 := $((3!! - 1) \times (F(6) + 36))$
31638 := $(F(3) \times ((1 + F(F(6))) \times 3!! - (F(8))))$
31639 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(16) \times F(F(3!))) - F(9)))$
31644 := $(F(3!) - ((1 - 6!) \times 44))$
31664 := $((3!! \times (1 + F(F(6)))) - F(6)) \times F(F(4))$
31667 := $((F(3) \times ((1 + F(F(6))) \times 6!)) - F(7))$
31668 := $((F(3) \times ((-1 - 6!) \times 6)) + 8!)$
31673 := $((F(F(3!)) \times F(16)) + F((7 \times 3)))$
31674 := $((3! + F(F((1 + 6)))) + (7!)) \times (F(4))!$
31678 := $((F(3) \times ((-1 + 6!) - 7!)) + 8!)$
31679 := $-(((3!! - 1) - (F(6))!) + (F(F(7)) \times F(9)))$
31680 := $((F(3) \times ((1 \times 6)!)) \times (F(8) + 0!))$
31682 := $(F(3) \times (1 + (6! \times (F(8) + F(2))))$
31683 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (F(F((1 + 6))) \times F((8 + 3))))$
31686 := $((F((F(3!) + 1)) \times F((-6) + F(8))) + F(F(F(6))))$
31694 := $(3! - (F(F((1 + 6))) \times (F(9) \times (-4))))$
31704 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + (-1 - F((F(7) + 0!)))) \times F(4))$
31707 := $(3 \times (F(F((1 + 7))) - F((0! + F(7))))$
31724 := $((3!! + 1) \times ((F(7) - 2) \times 4))$
31732 := $((-(((3! - 1))! - (7!))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 2$
31736 := $((F(3!))! - (-(((-1 + F(7))!)/F(F(3!))))/6!)$
31737 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + (-1 + 7!)) \times F(3)) - F(F(7))$
31739 := $((F(3!))! - (1 + ((F(7))!/(F(3) \times 9!))))$
31743 := $((F(3!) + 1) \times (-F(F(7)) - ((F(4))!)) + (F(3!))!)$
31752 := $(F(3) \times ((-((1 - 7)) + 5!)^2))$

$$\begin{aligned} 31753 &:= -(((F(3!))! - (1 - (((F(7))! / (-5!)) / 3!))) \\ 31764 &:= (((((3! + 1))! + F(F(7))) + F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) \\ 31772 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) - ((-1 - F(F(7))) \times F((F(7) - 2)))) \\ 31773 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (17 \times F((F(7) - F(3)))) \\ 31776 &:= (((F(3)^{1+7}) + 7!) \times 6) \\ 31780 &:= ((F(3!) - F(17)) \times (-F(8) - 0!)) \\ 31795 &:= (F((F(F(3!)) - 1)) + ((7! - F(9)) \times 5)) \\ 31824 &:= (3 \times ((1 + (F(8)^2)) \times 4!)) \\ 31826 &:= ((3!! + (((1 \times 8))! / 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 31837 &:= (F((-((3 + 1)) + F(8))) + (3! \times 7!)) \\ 31848 &:= ((3 \times (-1 + F(F(8)))) - F((4! - 8))) \\ 31854 &:= ((3 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) - F((-5) + F(F((F(4))!)))) \\ 31863 &:= ((F(F(3!)) + (1 + F(8))) \times (F(F(6)) + 3!)) \\ 31878 &:= (3! \times ((-((1 - 8)))! + (F(7) \times F(8)))) \\ 31894 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (((-((1 - 8)))! \times (-F(9))) / (-4))) \\ 31920 &:= ((F(F(3!)) - 1) \times (F((F(9) / 2)) - 0!)) \\ 31927 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F((F(9) / 2))) - F(7)) \\ 31930 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (((1 + F(9))^3 + 0!))) \\ 31934 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(19) \times F(3)) + 4!)) \\ 31935 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F((F(9) / F(3)))) - (5)) \\ \\ 31940 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 0 \\ 31941 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 1 \\ 31942 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 2 \\ 31943 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 3 \\ 31944 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 4 \\ 31945 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 5 \\ 31946 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 6 \\ 31947 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 7 \\ 31948 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 8 \\ 31949 &:= (F(F(3!)) - 1) \times F(F(9) / F(F(4))) + 9 \\ \\ 31953 &:= (-(((F(3) \times F(19)) + (5))) + (F(3!))!) \\ 31956 &:= (((F(F(3!)) + (F(19))) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 31958 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(19) \times F(-((5 - 8)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 31960** := $((F(F(3!)) - 1) \times (F((9 + F(6))) + 0!))$
31964 := $((-(F(3) \times F(19))) + (F(6))! + (F(4))!)$
31966 := $(-((F(3) \times F(19)) - F(6))) + (F(6))!$
31970 := $(F(3) \times (F(F(-(1 - 9)))) + (7! - 0!))$
31971 := $((F(3) \times (F(F(-(1 - 9)))) + (7!)) - 1)$
31972 := $((((3! + 1))! + F((F(9) - F(7)))) \times 2)$
31973 := $(F(F(3)) + ((F(F(-(1 - 9)))) + (7!)) \times F(3))$
31974 := $(3! \times ((1 + (9!/7!))^{F(F(4))}))$
31994 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - ((1 \times 9))!)/(-9 - F(F(4))))$
32045 := $(-((3!! + (2 + 0!))) + (F((F(4))!)^5))$
32046 := $(-(3!!) - ((2 + 0!) \times (4! - F(F(F(6))))))$
32054 := $(3! + ((F(((2 + 0!)!)^5) - ((F(4))!)))$
32056 := $(F(3!) + ((F(((2 + 0!)!)^5) - (6!)))$
32076 := $(-(3) \times (F(F(((2 + 0!)!)) + (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))))))$
32118 := $-((3!! - ((2 + 1) \times F(F((1 \times 8))))))$
32124 := $-((3!! - ((F(21) + 2) \times F(4)))$
32127 := $((F((3 \times 2)))! + (-1 - (2^{F(7)})))$
32128 := $((F(3) \times (-2^{12})) + 8!)$
32129 := $((3!/(-2)) - 1) \times (-F((2 + 9)))$
32133 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - (2 + F(13))) \times 3)$
32134 := $((F(3!))! - ((2^{13}) - (F(4))!))$
32136 := $((3! + F(21)) \times 3) - 6!$
32137 := $(-F(3) - (-((2 + 1) \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(7))))))$
32147 := $(F(3!) - (-((2 + 1) \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - F(F(7))))))$
32167 := $((3!^2)/16 - F(F(7)))$
32184 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - 218) \times F(4))$
32193 := $((F(F(3!)))^2 \times (1 + (9 \times F(3!))))$
32235 := $(-((F(F(3!)) + ((-((2 + 2)) \times (F(3!))!)/5)))$
32242 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - ((22^{F(4)}) \times (-2)))$
32244 := $(3! \times (-2) - (-((2^{F(4)!}) \times F(F((F(4))!))))$
32253 := $((((F(3!))! \times (-2 + 2))/(-5)) - 3)$
32254 := $((((F(3!))! \times (-2 + 2))/(-5)) - F(F(4)))$
32255 := $((((F(3!))! \times (-2 + 2)) + (5))/(-5))$
32256 := $(F((3! \times 2)) \times (2 \times (5! - F(6))))$

- 32258** := $(F(3) - (((F((F((2 + 2))))!)!)/5) - 8!)$
32262 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (((2 + F((2 \times 6)))^2)))$
32264 := $(((3! \times (-(2 + 2))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4)$
32268 := $(3! \times (2 + ((2^{F(6)}) \times F(8))))$
32295 := $((F(F(3!)) - (((F((2 + 2))))!)! \times 9)) \times (-5)$
32304 := $((((F(3!))!/2) + (((3 + 0!))!)!/(F(F((F(4))!))))!)$
32320 := $((F(3!))! - ((-F(2)) + F(F(3!)))^{2+0!})$
32326 := $((((F(F(F(3!))) - (2^{F(3!)})) \times 2) + F(F(F(6))))$
32327 := $-(((F(F(3!)))^2) - (F(3)^{2+F(7)}))$
32329 := $((((F(F(F(3!))) + F(2)) \times 3) - (2^9))$
32334 := $((3 \times F(F(2^3))) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-4!)))$
32335 := $((F(3!))! - (F((23 - 3!)) \times 5))$
32338 := $((((F(3!))! - 2) - ((F(F(3!))!)!/((-3) + F(8))))!$
32339 := $((((F(3!))! - F(2)) - ((F(F(3!))!)!/(F(3) \times 9)!))$
32343 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - (F((2 + F(3!))) \times F(4))) \times 3)$
32344 := $-((F(3!) - (2 \times (3!! + (F(4!)/F(4))))))$
32345 := $-((F((F(3!) + 2)) + (3!! \times (-45))))$
32352 := $(F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))) + (((F(F(3)) + 5!)^2)))$
32354 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - (((F(2) - F(F(F(3!)))) + 5!) \times (-4))))$
32358 := $(-(((3 + 2)! - (3 \times (5! - F(F(8))))))$
32364 := $(((3! \times 2) \times (3^{F(6)})) - F(4!))$
32367 := $(3 \times ((-F((2 \times 3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(7))$
32370 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - (-2) \times (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(F(7)) + 0!))))$
32371 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - ((-2) \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(7)))) + 1)$
32373 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + F(2)) - ((F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(3))))$
32374 := $((F(3!))! - ((F((F(2) + F(3!))) \times F(F(7))) + (4!)))$
32376 := $(((-3!) - F((2 \times F(3!)))) + (7!)) \times F(6)$
32377 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(2) + F((F(3) + F(7)))) \times F(7)))$
32378 := $(((3!! + 2) \times (F(3) - F(7))) + 8!)$
32379 := $((((F(3!))! + 2) - F(F(3!))) - (F(F(7)) \times F(9)))$
32382 := $((F(3!))! - (2 \times ((3 \times F(8))^2))$
32384 := $((F(3!)^2) \times (F(3) + (F(8) \times 4!)))$
32385 := $(((3!!/2) + F(F(3!))) \times 85)$
32387 := $((((3 + 2)! - F(3)) + F(8)) \times F(F(7)))$

- 32392** := $(-(F(3!)) + (((-F(2)) + F(F(3!))) \times 9)^2)$
32394 := $((3!! \times ((2 + 3) \times 9)) - (F(4)!))$
32395 := $((F(F(3)) - (((2 \times 3)!) \times 9)) \times (-5))$
32396 := $((3!! + F(F((F(2) + 3!)))) \times F(9)) - 6$
32397 := $((F((3 \times 2)))! - F(F(3))) + (-F(9) \times F(F(7)))$
32398 := $((F(((3! + F(2)) + 3!)) \times (-F(9))) + 8!)$
32399 := $(-(3) - ((F((2 \times F(3!))) - F(9)) \times (-F(9))))$
32403 := $((F(3!))! - (F((2 \times ((F(4))! + 0!))) \times F(F(3!))))$
32405 := $((((3^2) \times ((F(4))!)!) + 0!) \times 5)$
32406 := $(3 \times ((F((2 \times (F(4))!)) \times (-0!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
32409 := $((3!! \times (-2 - F(4)) - 0!) \times (-9))$
32411 := $((F(3!))! + ((-F(2)) + ((F(4))!)!) \times (-11))$
32412 := $(3 \times ((2 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - F(12)))$
32416 := $((F(3!) \times (-F((2^4)) + 1)) + (F(6))!)$
32423 := $((F(3!))! - (F(2) - (-F((4^2))) \times F(3!)))$
32426 := $((F(3!) \times (-F((2^4)))) + 2) + (F(6))!$
32433 := $((F(F(3!)) - 2) \times (F((4^{F(3)})) + 3!))$
32434 := $(F((3^2)) - ((-4!) - F(F(3!))) \times ((F(4))!))$
32435 := $((-F(F((3! + F(2)))) - ((F((F(4))!)!)/(-3!)) \times 5)$
32436 := $((3!^2) - ((4! + F(F(3!))) \times (-6!)))$
32437 := $((F((3! + F(2)))^{F(4)} + (3! \times 7!))$
32438 := $(-(((F(F(3!)) - F(2))^{F(F(4))}) - (3 \times F(F(8))))$
32439 := $((F((F(3!) \times 2)) - 4) \times (-F(F(3)) - F(9)))$
32442 := $((F(F(3!)) \times 2) + (((F(4))!)!/4^2))$
32443 := $(-F(3) + ((F(2) + ((F(4))!)!) \times (4! + F(F(3!))))$
32444 := $(-(((F(3)) + ((F(2) + (4))!)^{F(F(4))}) - F(4!)))$
32445 := $((3!! + F(2)) \times ((F(4) \times F(4)) \times 5))$
32446 := $(F(F(3)) + ((F(2) + ((F(4))!)!) \times (4! + F(F(6))))$
32448 := $((F(3!)^2) \times (F(4) + (4! \times F(8))))$
32453 := $((3!! + F(2)) \times 45) + F(3!)$
32454 := $((F(3!) - F(F((2 \times 4)))) + 5!) \times (-F(4))$
32456 := $(-(((F(F(3!)) + F(2)) - (F(4) \times (-5! + F(F(F(6)))))))$
32457 := $(3 \times (F(F((2 \times 4))) - ((5! + (7))))$
32458 := $(-(F(F(3!)) - (F(2) - (F(4) \times (5! - F(F(8))))))$

- 32464** := $((F(3!)^2) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-F(F(6)) + (4!))))$
32465 := $(-F((3! + F(2)))) - (-F(4) \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5!))$
32466 := $((3!! + F(2)) \times (4! + F(F(6)))) + F(F(6))$
32467 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + 2) \times F(4) - F((F(F(6)) - 7)))$
32469 := $((3!! / (-2)) + ((F(4) \times F(F(F(6)))) - 9))$
32472 := $((F((F(F(3!)) - F(2))) \times (-4!)) / (-7 - 2))$
32475 := $(3 \times ((-F(2)) + F((F(4) \times 7))) - 5!)$
32478 := $(3 \times (F(F((2 \times 4))) - ((F(7) - 8))!))$
32481 := $(-3) \times (((F(2) + (4))!) - F(F(8))) - 1)$
32484 := $((F(3) - ((F(2) + (4))!) + F(F(8))) \times F(4))$
32485 := $((3!! + 2) \times (4! + F(8))) - (5)$
32486 := $((3!! / (-2)) + ((F(4) \times F(F(8))) + F(6)))$
32487 := $((F(F(3)) - ((F(2) + (4))!) \times (-F(8) \times F(7)))$
32488 := $((F(3!) \times (-F((2^4) - 8))) + 8!)$
32490 := $((3!! + 2) / F(F(4))) \times 90$
32495 := $((F(F(3)) - ((2 + ((F(4))!)!) \times (-9))) \times 5)$
32497 := $((3 \times ((-2) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - F(9))) - F(F(7))$
32533 := $(F((F(3!) + 2)) - ((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-3))$
32534 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((-2) + (5 \times 3!!)) \times (F(4))!)$
32535 := $(-F((3 + (2 \times 5)))) + (F(3!)^5)$
32536 := $((-(((3 \times 2)^5)) - F(3!)) + (F(6))!)$
32542 := $((-(((3 \times 2)^5)) + (F((F(4))!)!) - 2)$
32543 := $((-(((3 \times 2)^5)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(3))!)$
32545 := $((F(3))! - (-((F(2)^5!) + ((F(4))!^5)))$
32546 := $((-(((3 \times 2)^5)) + F(F(4))) + (F(6))!)$
32547 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (F(2) - (5 \times (((F(4))!)! - (7!))))$
32553 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - (-25 + 5!)) \times 3)$
32557 := $((F(3))! - (((F(2) + (5))^5) - F(7)))$
32563 := $((F((F(3!) + 2)) \times (-5)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3))$
32565 := $((F(3))! - (F((2 \times 5)) \times (F(F(6)) + 5!)))$
32568 := $((-3) \times F(-((2 - 5) \times 6))) + 8!$
32569 := $(-3) + ((-2) + (5! \times F(6))) \times F(9))$
32572 := $((F(F(F(3!))) \times 2) + (5! \times F((F(7) - 2))))$
32574 := $(3 \times ((2 + 5!) \times F((7 + 4))))$
32576 := $((F(3!) \times (-F(2) + 5!)) + (7!)) \times F(6))$

- 32584** := $-((F(F(3!)) + ((F(F((2 + 5))) - (F(F(8)) \times F(4))))))$
- 32589** := $(((((3 \times 2)! \times 5) + F(8)) \times 9)$
- 32593** := $((F(3!))! + F(2)) + (F((-((5 - 9)))!)/(-3!))$
- 32594** := $((F(3!))! + 2) + (F((-((5 - 9)))!)/(-F(4)!))$
- 32598** := $(3 \times (((F(2) + 5)))!)/(-9) + F(F(8)))$
- 32605** := $-((F(F((3! + F(2)))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times F(-((0! - (5))))))$
- 32607** := $((3 \times (F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) + (-0! - F(F(7))))$
- 32608** := $((3 \times (F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(-((0! - 8))))$
- 32624** := $-((F((3! \times 2)) - ((F(6)^{F(2)+4})))$
- 32634** := $(F(F(3!)) \times ((2^{F(6)} + 3) \times (F(4)!))$
- 32637** := $((F(F(3!)) + 2) \times (6! + (3 \times F(F(7))))$
- 32638** := $(((-((F(3!)^2) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3) - 8)$
- 32639** := $((F((F(3!) + 2)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-3)) - F(9))$
- 32640** := $((F((3^2)) \times F(6)) \times ((4 + 0)!))$
- 32643** := $(((-((F(3!)^2) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(4)) - 3)$
- 32644** := $(((-((F(3!)^2) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(4)) - F(F(4)))$
- 32645** := $((F(3!)^{-F(2)+6} - ((F(4) + 5!)))$
- 32646** := $((3 \times F(F((2 + 6)))) - (4! \times F(6)))$
- 32647** := $((F(F(3!)) \times 2) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(4))) + F(F(7))))$
- 32648** := $-((((3 + 2)! + ((F(6)^4) \times (-8))))$
- 32649** := $((3 \times F(F((2 + 6)))) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times 9))$
- 32652** := $(3 \times ((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5!/2))$
- 32654** := $(-((((3 + 2)! - (F(6)^5))) + (F(4)!))$
- 32655** := $((3! + F(2)) + ((F(6)^5) - 5!))$
- 32656** := $-((((3 + 2)! - ((F(6)^5) + F(6))))$
- 32659** := $(F(F(3!)) - (2 - ((F(6) \times 5!) \times F(9))))$
- 32660** := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((F((2 \times F(6))) \times (F(F(6)) + 0!)))$
- 32663** := $(F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))) + (F(F(6)) \times (6! - F(3!))))$
- 32664** := $-((F(3!) \times (F((F(2) + 6))) - (F(6)^4))$
- 32674** := $(F((3^2)) \times ((F(6) + F(F(7))) + ((F(4)!))!))$
- 32677** := $((F(3!)^{-F(2)+6} + (-7) \times F(7))$
- 32678** := $(3!! + ((-2) \times F((6 + F(7)))) + 8!))$
- 32679** := $((F((3! \times 2)) \times (-6) + F(F(7)))) - 9)$
- 32682** := $(3! \times (-26) - (F(F(8))/(-2)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 32684 &:= ((F(3!)^{-F(2)+6}) - 84) \\ 32692 &:= (3!! - (-2) \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((9 - 2)!))) \\ 32695 &:= (F((F(3!) + 2)) + (((F(6) \times F(9)) \times 5!)) \\ 32704 &:= (-((F(3!) - (2^{F(7)-0!}))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\ 32715 &:= ((3 \times (-F(2)) + F(F((7 + 1)))) - 5!) \\ 32725 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times 2) + F(F(7))) \times (-F(2) - 5!)) \\ 32728 &:= -((3!! + (-((F(2) + (7))) \times F((-2) + F(8)))))) \\ 32732 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)} - (3!^2)) \\ 32733 &:= (-3) + ((F(27) - F(3))/3!) \\ 32735 &:= ((F(3!) - (F(27)))/(3!/(-5!)) \\ 32737 &:= (3 + ((-2) + (7!/F(3))) \times F(7)) \\ 32738 &:= (((F(3!))! - (2^{F(7)})) + F(-((3! - F(8)))))) \\ 32741 &:= (F((F(F(3!)) - 2)) + (((F(7)^4) - 1))) \\ 32742 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)} - (4! + 2)) \\ 32743 &:= (3! + ((F(27) + (4))/3!)) \\ 32745 &:= ((3 - (2 \times F(7))) + (F((F(4)!))^5)) \\ 32752 &:= (F(3!) \times ((2^{7+5}) - 2)) \\ 32754 &:= (3! + (((2^{F(7)}) - (5)) \times 4)) \\ 32755 &:= ((F(F((3 \times 2))) \times (F(7) \times 5!)) - (5)) \\ 32756 &:= (((F(3) - F(27)) - 5!)/(-6)) \\ 32758 &:= ((-3) + F(2)) + ((F(7) \times 5!) \times F(8)) \\ 32762 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)} - ((6/2)!)) \\ 32770 &:= (F(3) \times ((2^{7+7}) + 0!)) \\ 32773 &:= (((F(3) \times F(2)) + 7!) \times F(7))/F(3) \\ 32775 &:= ((3! + F(2)) + (F((-7) + F(7)))^5) \\ 32777 &:= ((F((3! \times 2)) \times (F(F(7)) - 7)) + F(F(7))) \\ 32780 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F((2 \times 7)) \times (F(8) - 0!)) \\ 32783 &:= ((F(3)^{2+F(7)} + (F(8) - 3!)) \\ 32784 &:= (((((3 + 2)! \times F(7)) \times F(8)) + 4!) \\ 32787 &:= ((3! + (2^{7+8})) + F(7)) \\ 32793 &:= (((-3!) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))) - 9) \times 3) \\ 32794 &:= (((F(3)^{2+F(7)} + F(9)) - F((F(4)!)) \\ 32802 &:= (((3! \times (-2)) + F(F(8))) \times (0! + 2)) \\ 32803 &:= (-32) + ((F(F(8)) - 0!) \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32809 &:= ((3 \times (2 + F(F(8)))) - (0! + F(9))) \\ 32813 &:= (((3 \times (-F(2)) + F(F(8)))) - 1) - F(F(3!)) \\ 32814 &:= ((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) - ((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 32815 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - (-2 + (F(F(8)) \times F(-((1 - 5)))))) \\ 32817 &:= -((((3 \times 2)! - (F(8) \times F(17)))) \\ 32820 &:= ((-3!) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times (2 + 0!) \\ 32822 &:= ((F(3!) \times (-2)) + (F(F(8)) \times F((2 + 2)))) \\ \\ 32830 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 0 \\ 32831 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 1 \\ 32832 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 2 \\ 32833 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 3 \\ 32834 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 4 \\ 32835 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 5 \\ 32836 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 6 \\ 32837 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 7 \\ 32838 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 8 \\ 32839 &:= 3 \times F(F(2) \times F(8)) - F(3!) + 9 \\ \\ 32840 &:= ((F(3) + F((-2) + F(8))) + F((4! - 0!))) \\ 32841 &:= ((3 + F((-2) + F(8))) + F((4! - 1))) \\ 32845 &:= ((F(3!) + ((F(2) + 8)^4)) \times 5) \\ 32848 &:= (F(3!) \times (2 + ((8^4) + 8))) \\ 32850 &:= (((F(3) + 2) + F(F(8))) \times F((5 - 0!))) \\ 32851 &:= (F((3! + F(2))) + (F(F(8)) \times F((5 - 1)))) \\ 32852 &:= (F(3!) + ((2 + F(F(8))) \times (5 - 2))) \\ 32857 &:= ((F(3) + 2) + ((F(8) + 5!) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 32859 &:= (((3! + F(2)) + F(F(8))) \times F(-((5 - 9)))) \\ 32860 &:= (((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + F(F(6))) + 0!) \\ 32862 &:= ((F(3!) + F((F(2) \times F(8)))) \times (6/2)) \\ 32866 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (2 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(6) + (6)))) \\ 32867 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + ((2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6))) + F(7))) \\ 32870 &:= ((3 \times ((-2) + F(F(8))) + F(7)) - 0!) \\ 32874 &:= (((3! \times (-2)) - F(F(8))) \times (-7 - 4)) \\ 32876 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (2 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7) + (6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$32880 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 0$$

$$32881 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 1$$

$$32882 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 2$$

$$32883 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 3$$

$$32884 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 4$$

$$32885 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 5$$

$$32886 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 6$$

$$32887 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 7$$

$$32888 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 8$$

$$32889 := F(F(F(3!))) + 2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(8)) + 9$$

$$32890 := ((3 \times (-F(2)) + F(F(8)))) + F((9 + 0!))$$

$$32893 := (F((F(3!) + 2)) + (F(F(8)) \times (9/3)))$$

$$32894 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (2 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(9)) - (F(4)!)))$$

$$32895 := ((F(F(3)) - (2^8)) \times (-9 - 5!))$$

$$32898 := -((F(3!) - ((2 \times (F(F(8)) + F(9))) + F(F(8))))$$

$$32904 := (((F(F(3!)) + F(2)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))) \times F(4))$$

$$32906 := (F(F(F(3!))) - (2 \times (-F(9) - F(F(F(06))))))$$

$$32908 := (F(F(F(3!))) - (2 \times (-((F(9) + 0!) - F(F(8))))))$$

$$32924 := (-(((-3) + F((2 + 9)))^2)) + (F((F(4)!))!)$$

$$32925 := ((F(F(F(3!))) + 29) \times (-2 - 5))$$

$$32932 := (((F(F(F(3!))) + (-2 + F(9))) \times 3) - 2)$$

$$32933 := (((F(F(F(3!))) + 29) \times 3) + F(3!))$$

$$32934 := (3 \times ((-2) + F(9)) + F((-3) + 4!))$$

$$32936 := (F(3!) \times ((2^{9+3}) + F(F(6))))$$

$$32938 := (((F(F(F(3!))) + (2 + F(9))) \times 3) - 8)$$

$$32943 := (3 \times ((F(2) + F(9)) + F((4! - 3))))$$

$$32949 := (((F(F(3!))^2) - 9!) / (-F(F(4)) + 9))$$

$$32954 := ((3 \times F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))) + (5! - (4)))$$

$$32955 := (((3!! - F(2)) \times 9) + 5!) \times 5$$

$$32963 := ((F(F(3!)) + 2) + ((F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3))$$

$$32973 := (((F(3!)! / (-2)) - (F((9 + F(7))) \times (-3)))$$

$$32974 := -((F(F(F(3!))) - (-((2 - (9 \times 7))) \times ((F(4)!))!))$$

$$32975 := (F((F(F(3!)) + 2)) + (F(9) \times (7 + 5!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32976 &:= (((F(3!) + F((2 \times 9))) \times F(7)) - (6!)) \\
 32978 &:= (((F(3!)!)/2) - (-F(9)) \times F((-7) + F(8)))) \\
 32983 &:= -((3! - ((F(2) - 9!)/(-8 + 3)))) \\
 32985 &:= ((3 \times ((F(2) \times 9) + F(F(8)))) + 5!) \\
 33003 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) + F((F(3!) + (0! + 0!)))) \times 3) \\
 33024 &:= ((F(3!)^{3!-0!}) + (2^{F(F(4)!)})) \\
 33033 &:= (((F(3)^{3!}) + 0!) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3) \\
 33036 &:= (3 \times (((F(F(3!)) + 0!) \times 3) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 33037 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F((0! + F(3!))) - F(F(7)))))) \\
 33038 &:= -((((3^{F(3!)} + 0!) + 3!!) - 8!)) \\
 33039 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - ((0! - (F(3) \times F(9)))))) \\
 33042 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F((0! + F((F(4)!))) \times 2)))) \\
 33043 &:= (((F(3!)! - F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) - (F((F(4)!)^3))) \\
 33047 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((0 - 4!) + F(F(7)))) \\
 33054 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((0! + (5))^{F(4)})) \\
 33055 &:= (F((F(3) + F(3!))) \times (0! - (5! \times (-5)))) \\
 33063 &:= ((-F(3!)) + F(F((3! + 0!))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3)) \\
 33065 &:= (-3!!) - ((-F(3!)) + F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-5)) \\
 33067 &:= (-F(F(3))) + ((3 \times (-0!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \\
 33068 &:= ((3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!)) + F(-((F(6) - F(8)))))) \\
 \\
 33070 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 0 \\
 33071 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 1 \\
 33072 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 2 \\
 33073 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 3 \\
 33074 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 4 \\
 33075 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 5 \\
 33076 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 6 \\
 33077 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 7 \\
 33078 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 8 \\
 33079 &:= 3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 0! + F(F(7)) + 9 \\
 \\
 33081 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (0 - 81))) \\
 33088 &:= ((F((3! + F(3!))) - 0!) \times 88) \\
 33094 &:= ((F(3)^{F(3!)} + (F(F(-(0! - 9)))) \times F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 33096** := $((F(F(3!)) - F((F(3!) + 09))) \times (-F(F(6))))$
- 33097** := $((F(3!))! - ((-3) + F(09)) \times F(F(7)))$
- 33099** := $-((F(F(3!)) - (3!! \times (F((0! + 9)) - 9))))$
- 33105** := $-((3!! - (F((F(3) \times 10)) \times 5)))$
- 33107** := $((F(3!))! + ((3!! \times (-10)) - F(7)))$
- 33108** := $(3 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) + ((10)!/8!))$
- 33110** := $((F(3!))! + ((3!! + 1) \times (-10)))$
- 33113** := $(F(3!) + ((F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(11))) \times 3)$
- 33114** := $((F(F(F(3!)))) + (3 + F(11))) \times F(4)$
- 33117** := $-((F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(3!)) - (1 + F(17)))))$
- 33124** := $((((3!!/F(3!)) + 1)^2) \times 4)$
- 33126** := $(3 \times ((F(3!) \times 12) + F(F(F(6)))))$
- 33135** := $((F(3) + F(F((3! + 1)))) \times (F(F(3!)) + 5!))$
- 33137** := $((F(F(F(3!))) + (F(F(3!)) + 1)) \times 3) + F(F(7))$
- 33143** := $((3!! \times (-F(3))) - 1) \times (-4!) + F(F(3))$
- 33144** := $((3!! \times (F(3) \times (-1 + 4!))) + 4!)$
- 33145** := $(F((3! + F(3!))) + (F((F((1 \times 4)))!)^5))$
- 33147** := $(3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + ((-1 - ((F(4)!)/(-7)))))$
- 33153** := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (15 \times F(F(3!))))$
- 33156** := $(3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (1 - (-5) \times F(F(6))))))$
- 33174** := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((1 + F(7)) \times 4!))$
- 33176** := $((3 + F(3!)) \times F((1 + F(7)))) \times F(6)$
- 33178** := $((F(3!))! - F((F(F(3!)) - 1)) - (F((-7) + F(8))))$
- 33189** := $((3 \times (((3! - 1))! + F(F(8)))) - 9)$
- 33195** := $(3 \times ((-F(F(3))) + F(F(-(1 - 9)))) + 5!)$
- 33198** := $(3 \times ((-((3 + 1) - 9))! + F(F(8))))$
- 33204** := $(3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (2 + ((0! + 4))!)))$
- 33207** := $((F(3!) \times (F((F(F(3!)) - 2)) - 0!)) - F(F(7)))$
- 33214** := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F(2) - F(14))))$
- 33215** := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + F(-(F(2) - 15)))$
- 33216** := $((F(3!))!/(-3) + (((2 + 1))!^6))$
- 33217** := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (2 + F((1 + F(7)))))$
- 33234** := $(((-3!) \times (F(F(3!)) + F(2))) - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-F(4))$
- 33235** := $((F(3) + F(F(3!))) \times ((2 \times 3!!) + 5))$
- 33237** := $(3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (((2 + 3))! + F(7))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 33238 &:= (((-F(F(3))) + F(F(3!)))^2) + (3 \times F(F(8)))) \\ 33243 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times (-2)) + F(4!)) - 3 \\ 33244 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times (-2)) + F(4!)) - F(F(4)) \\ 33246 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times (-2)) + (F(4 \times 6))) \\ 33247 &:= ((F(3!) \times (F((F(F(3!)) - 2)) + 4)) - F(F(7))) \\ 33248 &:= ((F((-F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) - (F(2) + 4!)) \times 8 \\ 33249 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(2) + (4 \times F(9)))) \\ 33250 &:= ((3!! - F((F(3!) + 2))) \times 50) \\ 33255 &:= (((3! + F((F(F(3!)) - F(2)))) - 5!) \times 5) \\ 33256 &:= ((F((-F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) - ((F(2) - (5))))! \times F(6) \\ 33258 &:= ((3 + 3!!) \times (25 + F(8))) \\ 33262 &:= (-3!!) + ((-3!!) + F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) \times 2) \\ 33264 &:= (((33 \times 2) \times F(F(6))) \times 4!) \\ 33265 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((3!! + (F(2) - (6^5)))) \\ 33266 &:= (((33 - 2) \times 6!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 33267 &:= ((-F(3!)) \times (F(F(3!)) - F((-2) + F(F(6)))) - F(7)) \\ \\ 33270 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 0 \\ 33271 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 1 \\ 33272 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 2 \\ 33273 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 3 \\ 33274 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 4 \\ 33275 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 5 \\ 33276 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 6 \\ 33277 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 7 \\ 33278 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 8 \\ 33279 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(-F(2) + F(7))) + 9 \\ \\ 33280 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 0 \\ 33281 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 1 \\ 33282 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 2 \\ 33283 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 3 \\ 33284 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 4 \\ 33285 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 5 \\ 33286 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33287 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 7 \\
 33288 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 8 \\
 33289 &:= F(3!) \times (-F(F(3!)) + F(-2 + F(8))) + 9 \\
 \\
 33291 &:= (3!! - (F((F(3!) \times 2)) \times (-F(9) - 1))) \\
 33294 &:= (((-F(3!)) + F((F(3!) \times 2))) \times F(9)) + F((F(4)!)) \\
 33304 &:= (((F(3!) + 3!!) + 3!!) \times (-0! - 4!)) \\
 33306 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (-((3!! \times F((3! + 0!)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 33317 &:= (-F(3)) + ((F((F(3) \times 3!)) - 1) \times F(F(7))) \\
 33318 &:= (3 \times ((F(3!) \times (F(F(3!)) - 1)) + F(F(8))) \\
 33322 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^2)) \\
 33325 &:= (((F(3!))!/3!) - F((F(3!) + 2))) \times 5 \\
 33327 &:= (F(3!) + ((F((F(3) \times 3!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 33328 &:= ((3!!/(-3!)) + (F(3!) \times F((-2) + F(8)))) \\
 33329 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F(F(3!)) - (2^9)))) \\
 33330 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(F((F(F(3)) + 3!))) \times 30)) \\
 33333 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) + (3 \times F((F(3) + F(3!)))) \times 3) \\
 33334 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (-F(3!) - (F(F(3!)) \times (-4!)))) \\
 33335 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times (3^3)) + (F(3!)^5)) \\
 33336 &:= (((F(3) + 3)^{3!}) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 33337 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(3!)^3) - F(7))) \\
 33341 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(F(3!)) \times 4!) - 1)) \\
 33342 &:= (3 \times ((F(3!) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F((4 \times 2)))) \\
 33343 &:= (((3!! + F(F(3!))) \times (F(F(3!)) + (4!))) - F(3)) \\
 33344 &:= ((F(3!)^{F(3)+3}) + (4! \times 4!)) \\
 33345 &:= ((3!! + F(F((3 + 3)))) \times 45) \\
 33346 &:= (((F(3!))! \times (-3!))/(-3!^4)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 33347 &:= (3 + (F(3!) \times (F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))) - F(7))) \\
 33348 &:= (((F(3!)^3) - F(3)) + (F(4) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 33349 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F(F(3)) - (F(F(4))^9))) \\
 33350 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(3!)^{F(5-0!)})) \\
 33354 &:= ((-3!) + F((F(3) \times F(3!)))) \times F((5 + 4)) \\
 33357 &:= (((((F(3!))!/(-3!)) + F(3)) \times (-5)) - F(F(7))) \\
 33359 &:= ((3!! - F(F(3))) + (F(3!) \times (5! \times F(9)))) \\
 33360 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(3!))!/F(F(3!))) + ((F(6) - 0!))!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 33363** := $(F(F(3!)) + (((-F(3!)) \times F(F(3!))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-3))$
33364 := $((((3 - 3!!) \times F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(F(4))))$
33365 := $((F(3!)^3) + (3 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (5))))$
33366 := $(3 \times ((F(3!) \times (F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
33367 := $(((((F((3 + 3)))!)/(-3!)) + (F(6)!)) - F(F(7)))$
33368 := $(F(3!) \times ((3!^{F(3)}) - F((F(6) + F(8))))$
33369 := $-((F(F((3 + 3))) \times (F(3!) - F((F(6) + 9))))$
33372 := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (3! \times F((F(7) - 2)))$
33373 := $(((((F(3!))!)/(-3!)) + (F(3!))!) - (F(F(7)) - 3!))$
33374 := $((F(3!) \times F((-F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) - 74$
33375 := $(F((3 + F(3!))) \times 375)$
33376 := $((-((3 \times 3)) + F((3! + F(7)))) \times F(6))$
33377 := $-(((F(3!) \times (F(3!) - F((3! + F(7)))) + 7))$
33378 := $((F(3!)^{F(3)+3}) + (F((7 + 8))))$
33379 := $(3 + (F(3!) \times (F((3! + F(7))) - 9))$
33382 := $(-F(3)) - (F(3!) \times (F(3!) - F((F(8) - 2))))$
33383 := $-((F(F(3)) + (F(3!) \times (F(3!) - F((F(8) - F(3))))))$
33384 := $((3 \times ((3!! \times (-3!)) - 8)) + F(4!))$
33385 := $((((F(F(3!)))^3) - F((-3) + F(8))) \times 5)$
33386 := $((((F(3!))! \times 3) - ((F(3!) \times F(F(8))) + 6))$
33387 := $(3 - (F(3!) \times (3!! + (-F(8)) \times F(F(7))))$
33390 := $((-3!) + F((3! + F(3!)))) \times 90$
33392 := $((F(3!))! + ((F(3!) - (3! \times (F(9)^2))))$
33393 := $(-F((F(3) \times 3!)) + (F(F(3!)) \times F((F(9)/F(3))))$
33394 := $((F(F(F(3!))) \times (-F(3!))) + (((3! + 9!)/F(4))))$
33396 := $((3! + 3!!) \times ((3! + F(9)) + (6)))$
33397 := $((F((3 \times 3!)) - (3! + 9)) \times F(7))$
33398 := $-(((F(3!)^{3!}) - ((3 \times 9) \times F(F(8))))$
33400 := $(F(3!) \times (-3!) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) - (0! + 0!))))$
33404 := $(-((F(3!))!) + ((-3!!) - F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!))) \times (-4))$
33405 := $((3^{F(3!)} + ((4 + 0!))!) \times 5)$
33407 := $-((F(F(3)) - (F((3 \times 4)) \times (-0!) + F(F(7))))$
33410 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - ((3!! - (F(4!)/(1 + 0!))))$
33411 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (-3!) + F(((F(4)! + 11))))$

- 33412** := $((F(F(F(3!))) - (-3!!) \times F((F(4)!))) \times (1 \times 2))$
33414 := $((F(3!) \times (3!! - 4!)) + 1) \times (F(4)!)$
33416 := $((3! \times (3!! - 4!)) + 1) \times F(6)$
33417 := $(3! + (F(F(3!)) \times (-((F(4)! - F(17))))))$
33419 := $(3 + (F(3!) \times (-4 + F(19))))$
33422 := $((F(3!) \times (-3 + F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 2)))) - 2)$
33423 := $(-F(F(3))) - (F(3!) \times (F(4) - F((-2 + F(F(3!))))))$
33424 := $(F(3!) \times (F((3 + 4^2)) - F(4)))$
33426 := $(3 \times (((F(3!) + (F(4)!))^2) + F(F(F(6)))))$
33427 := $-((F(F(3!)) - (F(3!) \times F((4! + (2 - 7))))))$
33428 := $((F(F(3)) - F(F(3!))) + (F((F(4)!)) \times F((-2 + F(8)))))$
33431 := $(((-F(3)) + F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))) \times F(3!)) - 1)$
33432 := $(F(3!) \times (-F(3) + F((4! - (3 + 2)))))$
33433 := $((F(3!) \times F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))) - (-3! + F(F(3!))))$
33434 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - ((3!! + ((F(4!)/(-F(3)) - 4!))))$
33435 := $((F(3!))! - (F(((3! + 4) \times F(3))) + 5!))$
33436 := $(-((F(3) \times 3!)) + (F((F(4)!)) \times F((-F(3) + F(F(6))))))$
33437 := $(F(F(3!)) + (F(3!) \times (-4 + F((3! + F(7))))))$
33438 := $(3 \times (((F(F(3)) + 4!) \times F(3!)) + F(F(8))))$
33439 := $((F(3!) \times F((3! + F((4 + 3)))) - 9)$

33440 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 0$
33441 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 1$
33442 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 2$
33443 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 3$
33444 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 4$
33445 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 5$
33446 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 6$
33447 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 7$
33448 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 8$
33449 := $-F(3!) + F(F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)! + 9$

33450 := $F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 0$
33451 := $F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 1$
33452 := $F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 2$

$$33453 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 3$$

$$33454 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 4$$

$$33455 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 5$$

$$33456 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 6$$

$$33457 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 7$$

$$33458 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 8$$

$$33459 := F(3) + F(3!) \times F(4! - 5) + 9$$

$$33460 := -((((-(F(3)) + F(F(3!)))^{F(4)} - ((F(6))! - 0!))))$$

$$33461 := ((((-(F(3)) + F(F(3!)))^{F(4)} - (F(6))!) \times (-1))$$

$$33462 := ((3! + F(3!)) + (F((F(4))!) \times F((F(F(6)) - 2))))$$

$$33463 := ((-3!) + F(F(3!))) + (F((F(4))!) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(3))))$$

$$33464 := ((F(3!)^{F(3)+F(4)} + (6! - 4!))$$

$$33465 := ((F(F(3)) + 3!!) - ((4! - (F(6)^5))))$$

$$33466 := (-F(3!)) - ((-3) + F((-4) + F(F(6)))) \times (-F(F(6)))$$

$$33467 := (3 + (F(3!) \times (F(F(4)) + F((6 + F(7))))))$$

$$33468 := (3 \times (((3!^{F(4)} - 6) + F(F(8))))$$

$$33469 := (F(F(3!)) + (F(3!) \times F(((4 + 6) + 9))))$$

$$33470 := (((F(3!))! + (F(3!)^4) - F(F((7 + 0!))))$$

$$33471 := ((F(3!) \times (3 + F((F(4))! + F(7)))) - 1)$$

$$33472 := (F(3!) \times (3 + F((4! - (7 - 2))))$$

$$33473 := (F(F(3)) + (F(3!) \times (F(4) + F((F(7) + 3!))))$$

$$33474 := (F(F((3 + 3))) \times (-F(4) + F((-7) + 4!)))$$

$$33475 := (((F(3!)^3) + F(4)) \times (F(7) \times 5))$$

$$33476 := -(((F(3) \times (3! - 4^7)) - 6!))$$

$$33477 := (((3!! - F(3!)) \times 47) + F(7))$$

$$33478 := (((F(3!))! \times (-3)) - (F(F(4)) + ((F(7))! / (-8!))))$$

$$33479 := (3!! - ((F(3) \times (-4^7)) + 9))$$

$$33480 := -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 0$$

$$33481 := -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 1$$

$$33482 := -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 2$$

$$33483 := -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 3$$

$$33484 := -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 4$$

$$33485 := -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33486 &:= -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 6 \\ 33487 &:= -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 7 \\ 33488 &:= -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 8 \\ 33489 &:= -(F(3)! + 3!!) / F(4)! + 8! + 9 \\ \\ 33494 &:= ((3!! + ((F(3)^{4!-9}))) + (F(4))!) \\ 33496 &:= (F(3!) \times (3! + F((4 + 9) + 6))) \\ 33508 &:= (3!! + ((F(3!)^5) - ((0! - F(8)))))) \\ 33509 &:= ((3!! + (F(3!)^5)) + F(-((0! - 9)))) \\ 33511 &:= (((F(3!)! / 3!) \times 5) - (F(11))) \\ 33512 &:= (F(3!) \times (F(3!) + F((F(F((5 + 1))) - 2)))) \\ 33520 &:= ((F(3!)! + (-35 - F(20))) \\ 33523 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times 5) - 2) + 3!! \\ 33524 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times 5) - F(2)) + ((F(4))!)! \\ 33525 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times 5) + ((F(2) + (5))))! \\ 33526 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times 5) + ((F(2) + 6!))) \\ 33527 &:= ((F((3 \times 3!)) - (5)) \times (F(2) \times F(7))) \\ 33529 &:= (-F(3!) + (F(F(3!)) \times F((F((5 - 2))! + 9)))) \\ 33531 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - ((3!! / 5) \times F(F((3! + 1)))))) \\ 33532 &:= (((F(3!)! - F(F(3!))) - (F((5! / 3!)) + 2)) \\ 33533 &:= (((3^{F(3!)}) \times 5) + F(3!)) + 3!! \\ 33534 &:= (((3 \times F(F(3 + 5)))) + 3!!) - (4!) \\ 33535 &:= (((F(3!)! / 3!) - F((5 + F(3)))) \times 5) \\ 33536 &:= ((F(3)^{F(3!)}) \times ((5^3) + 6)) \\ 33539 &:= (F(3) + (F(F(3!)) \times F((5 + 3) + 9))) \\ 33540 &:= (3 \times ((F(F(F(3!))) + F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) + 0!)) \\ 33542 &:= (3!! - (((F(F(F(3!))) - (5)) \times (-F(4))) + F(2))) \\ 33543 &:= (3!! + ((F(3!)^5) + F((4 + 3!)))) \\ 33544 &:= (F(3!) \times ((3! + F((-5) + 4!)) + (F(4))!)) \\ 33545 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((F(3) \times 5) + F((4 \times 5)))) \\ 33546 &:= ((-(3 \times 3) - F((5 \times 4))) + (F(6))!) \\ 33548 &:= ((F(F(3)) - F(3!)) - ((F((5 \times 4)) - 8!))) \\ 33549 &:= (3!! + ((F(F(3 + 5))) \times F(4)) - 9) \\ 33550 &:= (F((F(3) + F(3!))) \times F((5! / F((5 + 0!)))))) \end{aligned}$$

- 33551** := (((3!! × F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) / 5) - 1)
33553 := (F(((3 × 3) + 5)) × F((5 + 3!)))
33554 := -((F(F(3)) - (((3 + 5)! - F((5 × 4))))))
33555 := ((F((3 + 3)))! - F(((5 × 5) - 5)))
33556 := ((F(F(3)) + ((3 + 5)!) - F((5!/6)))
33557 := (-F(F(3))) + ((F(F(3!)) + 5!) × (5 + F(F(7))))
33558 := ((3 - F(((3 × 5) + 5))) + 8!)
33559 := (F(F(3)) - (F((3! + (5 + 5))) × (-F(9))))
33560 := ((F(3!))! - ((-3!) + F((5!/6))) + 0!)
33561 := ((F(3!))! - (-3!) + F((5!/(6 × 1))))
33562 := ((F(3!))! - ((-3!) + F((5!/6))) - F(2))
33563 := (((F((3 + 3)))! - F((5!/6))) + F(3!))
33564 := (((3 × F(F((3 + 5)))) + (6!)) + (F(4)!))
33565 := -((F((-F(F(3))) + F(F(3!)))) - ((5 + (F(6)!) + (5))))
33566 := ((3 × F(F((3 + 5)))) + ((F(6) + 6!))
33568 := -((F((3³)) - 5!) + (F(F(6)) × F(F(8))))
33569 := (3 + (((F(3!))! × (-5)) / (-6) - F(9))
33572 := (F(F(3!)) + (((3!!/5) × F(F(7))) - F(2))
33573 := (3!! + (3 × (5 + F((7 × 3))))
33574 := (-F(3)) + (((3!!/5) × F(F(7))) + (4!))
33576 := (F(3!) × (((-3) - 5!) + 7!) - 6!)
33577 := -((F(3) - ((-((3⁵)) + 7!) × 7))
33578 := -((F(F(3)) - (((3 + 5!) × F(7)) × F(8))))
33579 := (F(F(3!)) × (F(3) + F((-5) + F(7) + 9)))
33580 := (((F(3!))! / 3!) × 5) - (F(8) - 0!)
33581 := (((F(3!))! + F(F(3!))) - (-5) + F((F(8) - 1))))
33583 := ((F(3!))! - (-3) + ((5! + 8!) / 3!))
33584 := ((F(3!) × (-F(3))) + ((5 × 8!) / (F(4)!))
33586 := ((-3!) - F(3!)) + ((5 × 8!) / 6)
33587 := (F(3!) + (((3 + 5!) × F(8)) × F(7))
33590 := (((F(3!))! / 3!) × 5) - (9 + 0!)
33591 := (((F(3!))! / 3!) × 5) - (9 × 1)
33594 := (-3!) - ((3!! + 5!) × (-F(9) - (F(4)!)))
33595 := (((3! - (F(3!))!) × 5) / (-F((9 - 5)!))
33596 := (((F(3!))! / (-3!)) - (-((5 - 9) - (F(6)!))

$$33597 := (-3) + ((3!! + ((5! \times F(9)))) \times 7)$$

$$33598 := (((F(3)!)/(-3!)) - F(F(-((5 - 9)))) + 8!)$$

$$33599 := (((F(3)!)/3!) \times 5) - (9/9)$$

$$33600 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 00$$

$$33601 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 01$$

$$33602 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 02$$

$$33603 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 03$$

$$33604 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 04$$

$$33605 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 05$$

$$33606 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 06$$

$$33607 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 07$$

$$33608 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 08$$

$$33609 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 09$$

$$33610 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 10$$

$$33611 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 11$$

$$33612 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 12$$

$$33613 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 13$$

$$33614 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 14$$

$$33615 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 15$$

$$33616 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 16$$

$$33617 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 17$$

$$33618 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 18$$

$$33619 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 19$$

$$33620 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 20$$

$$33621 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 21$$

$$33622 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 22$$

$$33623 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 23$$

$$33624 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 24$$

$$33625 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 25$$

$$33626 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 26$$

$$33627 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 27$$

$$33628 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 28$$

$$33629 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 29$$

$$33630 := -F(3)!/3! + F(6)! + 30$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33631 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 31 \\ 33632 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 32 \\ 33633 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 33 \\ 33634 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 34 \\ 33635 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 35 \\ 33636 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 36 \\ 33637 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 37 \\ 33638 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 38 \\ 33639 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 39 \\ 33640 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 40 \\ 33641 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 41 \\ 33642 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 42 \\ 33643 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 43 \\ 33644 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 44 \\ 33645 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 45 \\ 33646 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 46 \\ 33647 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 47 \\ 33648 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 48 \\ 33649 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 49 \\ 33650 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 50 \\ 33651 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 51 \\ 33652 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 52 \\ 33653 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 53 \\ 33654 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 54 \\ 33655 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 55 \\ 33656 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 56 \\ 33657 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 57 \\ 33658 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 58 \\ 33659 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 59 \\ 33660 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 60 \\ 33661 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 61 \\ 33662 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 62 \\ 33663 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 63 \\ 33664 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 64 \\ 33665 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 65 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33666 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 66 \\ 33667 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 67 \\ 33668 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 68 \\ 33669 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 69 \\ 33670 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 70 \\ 33671 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 71 \\ 33672 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 72 \\ 33673 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 73 \\ 33674 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 74 \\ 33675 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 75 \\ 33676 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 76 \\ 33677 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 77 \\ 33678 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 78 \\ 33679 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 79 \\ 33680 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 80 \\ 33681 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 81 \\ 33682 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 82 \\ 33683 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 83 \\ 33684 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 84 \\ 33685 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 85 \\ 33686 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 86 \\ 33687 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 87 \\ 33688 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 88 \\ 33689 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 89 \\ 33690 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 90 \\ 33691 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 91 \\ 33692 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 92 \\ 33693 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 93 \\ 33694 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 94 \\ 33695 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 95 \\ 33696 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 96 \\ 33697 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 97 \\ 33698 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 98 \\ 33699 &:= -F(3!)/3! + F(6)! + 99 \end{aligned}$$

- 33702** := (((F(3) × F(F(F(3!)))) - (7! + 0!)) × 2)
- 33703** := (F((F(3) + F(F(3!)))) + ((7! + (03)!))
- 33704** := (F(3!) - (3! × ((F(F(7)) + 0!) × (-4!)))
- 33705** := (F(F(3!)) × (F(3!) + F(((F(7) - 0!) + (5))))
- 33706** := (F((F(3) + F(F(3!)))) + (((7! + 0!) + F(6)))
- 33714** := (3! × (3 - ((F(F(7)) + 1) × (-4!)))
- 33717** := (F(F(3!)) + (((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) × F((-1 + F(7))))))
- 33718** := ((3! × F(F(3!))) + (F(7) × F(18)))
- 33723** := ((F(3!))! - ((3!! + F(7)) × (F(2) + F(3!))))
- 33724** := (((3³) + 7!) + F(-(F(2) - 4!)))
- 33726** := (3! × (F((3! + F(7))) + (2 × 6!)))
- 33729** := (F((F(3) + F(F(3!)))) + (((7! - 2) + F(9))))
- 33730** := ((F(3!))! - ((3 × (F(7)³) - 0!))
- 33731** := (F((F(3) + F(F(3!)))) + (7! + F((F(3!) + 1))))
- 33732** := ((F(3!))! - (3 × ((F(7)³) - F(2)))
- 33733** := ((F(3!))! - ((F(3) × F(7)) + (3^{F(3!)})))
- 33734** := ((-F(3!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + ((7!/(-3)) + F(4!))
- 33735** := (((F(3!) × 3!!) + F((F(7) + 3))) × 5)
- 33736** := (F((F(3) × 3!)) + (F(7) × F((3 × 6))))
- 33737** := (((F((-F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) + 7) × F(3!)) + F(F(7))
- 33738** := ((3 × (3 - (F(7)³))) + 8!)
- 33739** := (F((F(3) + F(F(3!)))) - ((-7!) - F(3!) - F(9)))
- 33740** := (((F(3!))! / F(F(3!))) - F(F(7))) × (F(F((F(4)!)) - 0!))
- 33742** := (((F(3!) - (-3!) × F(F(7)))) × 4!) - 2)
- 33743** := ((F(3!) × (-F(3) - 7!)) - (F(4)^{F(3!)}))
- 33744** := ((3!! + (F(3) × (7^{F(4)}))) × 4!)
- 33745** := (((F(3!) + F(F(3!))) × F(F(7))) - F((F(4)!)) × 5)
- 33746** := ((3!! - F(3)) × ((F(7) × F(4)) + F(6)))
- 33747** := (((3!³) - 7!) + F(4)) × (-7)
- 33748** := -(((3^{F(3!)}) - (-((7 + 4) + 8!)))
- 33750** := (3 × ((F(3!) - F(F(7))) × (-50)))
- 33752** := (F(3) + (3! × (75²)))
- 33753** := (3 + (3! × (75^{F(3)})))
- 33754** := (-(((3 × (3⁷) + 5)) + (F((F(4)!))!))

$$\begin{aligned}
 33755 &:= (F(F(3!)) + ((F(3) \times (7^5)) + 5!)) \\
 33756 &:= ((-3) - (3^{F(7)-5})) + (F(6)!) \\
 33758 &:= -((F(F(3)) + (((3^{F(7)-5}) - 8!)))) \\
 33759 &:= -(((3^{F(3!)} - ((7!/5!) - F(9)))!) \\
 33760 &:= ((-((3 \times (3^7))) + (F(6)!) + 0!) \\
 33761 &:= ((F((3 \times 3!)) + F(7)) \times F((6 + 1))) \\
 33762 &:= ((3! + F((3 + F(7)))) \times F((F(6) + F(2)))) \\
 33763 &:= -((((3^{F(3!)} - 7) - (F(6)!) + 3)) \\
 33764 &:= -((((3^{F(3!)} - 7) - (F(6)!) + F(F(4)))) \\
 33765 &:= (F((-F(F(3))) + F(F(3!)))) + ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) \times 5!) \\
 33766 &:= -((((3^{F(3!)} - (7!/6!)) - (F(6)!) \\
 33768 &:= -((((((3 \times 3)! \times F(7))/6!) - 8!)) \\
 33769 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(3!) + ((-7) - 6!) \times (-9))) \\
 \\
 33770 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 0 \\
 33771 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 1 \\
 33772 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 2 \\
 33773 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 3 \\
 33774 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 4 \\
 33775 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 5 \\
 33776 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 6 \\
 33777 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 7 \\
 33778 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 8 \\
 33779 &:= 3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(7)) + 9 \\
 \\
 33780 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(3!) - F(F(7))) + F((F(8) - 0!)))) \\
 33782 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((3! - F(F(7))) + F((F(8) - F(2)))) \\
 33783 &:= (((3!! - F(3!)) + F(F(7))) + (F(F(8)) \times 3)) \\
 33784 &:= (F(3!) \times ((F(3) - 7!) + (F(8)^{F(4)})) \\
 33786 &:= ((3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(7))) + (F((8 + F(6)))) \\
 33787 &:= ((F((3 \times 3!)) + (7 + 8)) \times F(7)) \\
 33788 &:= (F((-F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) + (((F(F(7)) - F(F(8))) + 8!)) \\
 33789 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(F(3)) - ((F(7) + F((8 + 9)))))) \\
 33793 &:= ((3!! - F(F(3))) \times ((7 + F(9)) + 3!)) \\
 33794 &:= (F(3) - (F(3!) \times (-7! - (F(9) \times 4!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33795 &:= ((- (3!) + F((F(3) \times (-7)) + F(9)))) \times 5 \\
 33796 &:= ((F((3 \times 3!)) \times F(7)) - (F(9) \times (-6))) \\
 33797 &:= (3! + ((F((3 + F(7))) \times F(9)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 33798 &:= -((3!! + (3 \times ((7! / (-9)) - F(F(8)))))) \\
 33804 &:= (((F(3) + 3) \times F((F(8) - 0!))) - F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 33805 &:= (((F(3) - 3!) + F((F(8) - 0!))) \times 5) \\
 33808 &:= (((F(3!)! / 3!) - F(F(8))) \times (0 - 8)) \\
 33813 &:= (((3 + 3!!) \times (- (8 + 1))) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 33815 &:= (((3! / (-3)) + F((F(8) - 1))) \times 5) \\
 33819 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - (3!! \times (- (8) + F((1 + 9)))))) \\
 33820 &:= ((F(3) + 3) \times (F((F(8) - F(2))) - 0!)) \\
 33824 &:= -((((F(3!) \times (3! + 8))^2) - F(4!)) \\
 33827 &:= ((3!! \times ((3! \times 8) - F(2))) - F(7)) \\
 33828 &:= (3 \times ((3! \times F((8 + 2))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 33829 &:= -((F(F(3)) - ((F(3!) + (F((8 \times 2)))) \times F(9)))) \\
 33830 &:= ((F(3!) + F((F(3) \times 8))) \times F((F(3!) + 0!)) \\
 33831 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((F(F(3)) + 8) \times (3!! + 1))) \\
 33832 &:= -((F(3!) - (3!! \times ((8 \times 3!) - F(2)))) \\
 33833 &:= (F((F(3) \times F(3!))) + ((F(F(8)) \times 3) + F(3!)) \\
 33834 &:= (((3!! \times (3! \times 8)) - 3!!) - (F(4)!)) \\
 33837 &:= ((3!! \times (-F(3))) + ((8! - 3) - 7!)) \\
 33838 &:= (- (F(3)) + (((3!! \times (-8)) - 3!!) + 8!)) \\
 \\
 33840 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 0 \\
 33841 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 1 \\
 33842 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 2 \\
 33843 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 3 \\
 33844 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 4 \\
 33845 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 5 \\
 33846 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 6 \\
 33847 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 7 \\
 33848 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 8 \\
 33849 &:= 3!! \times (F(3) + F(8) + 4!) + 9 \\
 \\
 33853 &:= (- (3) + (((F(3!) \times 8) + 5!)^{F(3)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33854 &:= (-F(3)) + (((F(3!) \times 8) + 5!)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 33855 &:= ((3! + F(-((3! - F(8)) - (5)))) \times 5) \\
 33856 &:= ((F(3)^{F(3!)}) + ((8! \times 5)/6)) \\
 33858 &:= -(((3^{F(3!)}) + ((F(8) - 5!) - 8!))) \\
 33859 &:= ((F(((F(3) \times 3!) + 8)) \times 5) + F(9)) \\
 33861 &:= (F(F(3!)) + (3!! \times ((8 \times 6) - 1))) \\
 33862 &:= (3! + (((F(3) + F(8)) \times F(6))^2)) \\
 33865 &:= ((3!! + F((3! + 8))) + (F(6)^5)) \\
 33869 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(3!) + (F(8) + (6! \times (-9)))))) \\
 33873 &:= (((F((3 \times 3!)) + (F(8))) \times F(7)) + F(3!)) \\
 33878 &:= (F(3) \times (((3!! \times 8) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 33888 &:= ((3 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)))) + (F((8 + 8)))) \\
 33889 &:= ((F(3!) \times (F(3!) - F(F(8)))) + F((-8) + F(9))) \\
 33894 &:= -((3!! - (((3!! \times 8) + 9) \times (F(4)!))) \\
 33896 &:= (((F(3!))!/3!!) + (8! + (-9) \times 6!)) \\
 33912 &:= (((3!! - F(3!)) \times (-9)) + (F(((1 + 2)!))!) \\
 33913 &:= (((3!! - F(3!)) \times (-9)) + 1) + (F(3!))! \\
 33914 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times F((F(3!) + 9))) + (F(14))) \\
 \\
 33920 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 0 \\
 33921 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 1 \\
 33922 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 2 \\
 33923 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 3 \\
 33924 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 4 \\
 33925 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 5 \\
 33926 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 6 \\
 33927 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 7 \\
 33928 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 8 \\
 33929 &:= F(3!)! - (3!!/9)^2 + 9 \\
 \\
 33930 &:= ((3!!/F(3!)) \times F((9 + 3!) - 0!)) \\
 33932 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(3) \times F((F(9)/F(3)))) \times 2)) \\
 33933 &:= (((F(3!))! + F(F(3!))) - (9 \times (3!! - F(3!)))) \\
 33934 &:= ((F(3) + 3!!) \times (F(9) + F((3 + 4)))) \\
 33935 &:= (F((3! + F(3!))) + (F(9) \times F((F(F(3!)) - (5))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 33936** := $((F(3!) \times ((3! \times F(9)) - F(3))) \times F(F(6)))$
33937 := $((F(3!)! - (((F(3)^9) - F(F(3!))) \times F(7)))$
33939 := $((F(3!)! - ((3!! - (9 + F(3))) \times 9))$
33944 := $((F(3!)! - (((3!!/9)^{F(F(4))}) - (4!)))$
33945 := $((F((F(3) + (F(3) \times 9))) + (4!)) \times 5)$
33948 := $((((3!! \times (-F(3))) - F(9)) + F(4!)) - F(F(8)))$
33954 := $((((3!!/F(3!)) \times F((9 + 5))) + (4!))$
33955 := $((F(3!)! - ((3!! \times 9) + (5 - 5!)))$
33958 := $((-F(3)) + ((3!! \times (-9)) + ((5! + 8!))))$
33960 := $((F(3!)! - ((3!! \times 9) - ((6 - 0!)!))$
33963 := $((-(((3^{F(3!)} + (F(9) \times (-6)))) + (F(3!)!))$
33964 := $((F(3!)! - ((F(3!) - F((9 + F(6)))) \times (-4)))$
33965 := $((F((-F(F(3))) + F(F(3!)))) + (F(9) - (6))) \times 5)$
33966 := $((F(3!)! - ((3!! \times 9) - (6 \times F(F(6))))))$
33969 := $((((F(F(3!)) + F((F(3!) + 9))) \times F(F(6))) - 9)$
33973 := $((((3 + 3!!) \times (F(9) + F(7))) - F(3!))$
33974 := $((-F(3)) \times ((3!! - F((9 + F(7)))) + 4))$
33976 := $(((((F((3 + 3)))! / 9) - F(F(7))) \times F(6))$
33978 := $((F(F(3!)) + F((F(3!) + 9))) \times (F(7) + 8))$
33979 := $((F(F(3!)) \times F((F(3!) + 9))) + ((F(7) \times F(9))))$
33981 := $((3 + 3!!) \times (F(9) + F((8 - 1))))$
33982 := $((-F(3)) \times (((-((3 - 9)))! - F((F(8) + F(2))))))$
33983 := $((((3!! \times (-F(3) - F(9)))) + F(F(8))) - 3)$
33985 := $((-(3!!) - (F(3!)!)) + F(((9 + F(8)) - (5))))$
33986 := $((((3!! \times (-3) + F(9))) + F(F(8))) + (6!))$
33987 := $((3!! \times (3! \times 9)) + (-F(8) \times F(F(7))))$
33988 := $((F(3!)! - (-((F(3) - (9!/F(8)))) - F(F(8))))$
33990 := $((F(3!) + F((3! + 9))) \times F((9 + 0!)))$
33992 := $((((F(3!)! + ((3!! - F(9)) \times (-F(9)))) \times 2)$
33993 := $((F(3!) - (F(3!)!)) + (F((F(9) - 9)) - 3!!))$
33994 := $((((F((F(3) \times F(3!))) + F(9)) \times F(9)) - ((F(4!)!))$
33996 := $((3! \times ((3 - F(9)) \times F(9))) + (F(6)!))$
33997 := $((((-3!!) - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-F(9))) - (9! - F(F(7))))$
33998 := $(((((3!! - F(3!)) - F(9)) \times F(9)) + F(F(8)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33999 &:= (3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + ((9 + F(9)) \times 9))) \\
 34029 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(4!))! - F(F((0! + 2)!))) \times 9)) \\
 34034 &:= ((F(F(F(3!)))/F(F(4))) + (F((0! + 3!)^4)) \\
 34035 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(4))) + F((-0! + F(F(3!)))) \times 5) \\
 34036 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) \times F(F(4))) + (((0! + 3)!)/(F(F(6)!))) \\
 34038 &:= (3 \times (((F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!)^{F(3)} + F(F(8)))) \\
 34053 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) + 405) \times 3) \\
 34056 &:= (((-3) \times F(4!))/(0! - (5))) - (6!) \\
 34057 &:= (-F(F(3))) + ((F((F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!)) \times 5) + F(F(7))) \\
 34064 &:= ((F(3!)^{4+0!}) + (6^4)) \\
 34065 &:= (((3!^4) + 0!) + (F(6)^5)) \\
 34073 &:= ((-3!!) \times (F((F(4)!)) + 0!)) - (-F(F(7))) - (F(3!))! \\
 34086 &:= ((3! + 40) \times (F(8) + 6!)) \\
 34094 &:= (((3!/F(F(4))) + 0!) \times (-F(9))) + F(4!) \\
 34104 &:= ((3!! - 4!) \times (F(10) - (F(4)!)) \\
 34117 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(4!)/(1 + 1)) - F(7))) \\
 34124 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(4!)/(-1 \times 2)) + (F(4)!)) \\
 34125 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(4!)/(-1 \times 2)) + (5))) \\
 34126 &:= (((F(3!) - F(4!))/(-1 \times 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 34128 &:= (((3 - F(4!)) + 1)/(-2)) + F(F(8)) \\
 \\
 34130 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 0 \\
 34131 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 1 \\
 34132 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 2 \\
 34133 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 3 \\
 34134 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 4 \\
 34135 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 5 \\
 34136 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 6 \\
 34137 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 7 \\
 34138 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 8 \\
 34139 &:= F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/(-1 + 3) + 9 \\
 \\
 34142 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) - ((-4!) - F(((1 \times 4)!)))/2)) \\
 34143 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(((F(4)! + 1)) - (F(4!)/(-F(3)))))) \\
 34145 &:= (((F(3)^{F(4)!}) + F((-1 + F(F((F(4)!)))))) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 34146** := $((((3! \times F(4!)) - ((1 + (F(4)!))!)))/F(6))$
34153 := $((((F(3)!))! - ((F(4!) - (1 - 5!)))) + (F(3)!))!$
34154 := $(((((F(3)!))!/((F(4)!))!) \times F(15)) - (F(4)!))$
34155 := $(((((F(3)!))!/((F(4)!))!) \times F(15)) - (5))$
34157 := $((-3) + (F((F(4)!)) \times (F(15) \times 7)))$
34160 := $((((F(3)!))!/((F(4)!))!) \times F((16 - 0!)))$
34164 := $((((F(F(3!)))^{F(4)} + (-1 \times 6!)) \times 4)$
34167 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (-4 - (F(F((1 + 6))) \times (-7))))$
34168 := $(3!! + (F((4! + (1 - 6))) \times 8))$
34173 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (-4 + F(17))) + (3!!))$
34176 := $((F(3) \times 4!) \times (-((1 + 7)) + 6!))$
34179 := $((F(3!))! - ((4! - 1) \times (F(F(7)) + F(9))))$
34185 := $((((3 \times 4!) + F((-1 + F(8)))) \times 5)$
34193 := $((((F((3! \times F(4))) - 1) \times 9) + F(F(F(3!))))$
34223 := $((-((F(F(3)) - F(4!))) + (-(((2 + 2)!))!)/(F(F(3!))!))$
34226 := $((F(3) + F(4!)) + (-(((2 + 2)!))!)/(F(F(6))!))$
34230 := $((((-((F(3!))!) + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (-2)) - F(((3 + 0)!))!))$
34233 := $((3 - F(4!)) - (2 \times (F(F(3!)) - (F(3!))!))$
34234 := $(((((-(F(3!))!) + F(F((F(4)!)))) - 2) \times (-F(3))) - F(4!))$
34235 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(4!)/2) + (F(F(3!)) \times 5)))$
34236 := $((3!! - F(4!))/(-2^3)) \times 6$
34237 := $((3 + 4) \times (-2 + (F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7))))$
34238 := $(((((F(3!))! - F(4!)) - F((F(2) + F(3!)))) + 8!)$
34239 := $(((((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) - F(2)))) + (F(3!))!) - F(9))$
34243 := $(((((F(3!))! - 4) \times 2) - F(4!)) - F(F(3!)))$
34244 := $(((((F(3!))! - F(F(4))) \times 2) + (-4! - F(4!)))$
34245 := $((F(3!))! - ((4! + F(2)) \times (F(4)^5)))$
34246 := $((F(3!))! + ((-((4! + 2)) - F(4!)) + (F(6)!))$
34247 := $((-(F(3)) + F((4! - F(2)))) - (-4! \times F(F(7))))$

34248 := $((F(3!))! - ((4! + F(24)) - 8!))$
34250 := $F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 0$
34251 := $F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 1$
34252 := $F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 2$
34253 := $F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 3$

$$34254 := F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 4$$

$$34255 := F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 5$$

$$34256 := F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 6$$

$$34257 := F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 7$$

$$34258 := F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 8$$

$$34259 := F(F(F(3!))) + F(4!)/2 + 5! + 9$$

$$34262 := ((-3!) - F(4!)) + ((-2) + (F(6)!) \times 2)$$

$$34263 := ((3^{F(4)!}) \times (-F(2) - (F(6) \times 3!)))$$

$$34264 := (((F(3!) + F(4!))/(-2)) + (F(6)!) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$34265 := ((-F(3)) - F(4!)) + ((2 \times (F(6)!) - (5)))$$

$$34267 := ((F(3) - F(4!)) - ((-2) \times (F(6)!) + 7))$$

$$34268 := ((F(3!) - F(4!)) + (2 \times (-6) + 8!))$$

$$34269 := (-3) + (((4! \times 2) \times F(F(6))) \times F(9))$$

$$34270 := ((-F(3)) - F(4!)) - (-2) \times ((7 + 0!)!)$$

$$34271 := (3!! + ((F((4!/2)) \times F(F(7))) - 1))$$

$$34272 := ((3!! - (F(4)!) \times (-F(2) - ((7^2))))$$

$$34273 := (F(F(3)) + ((F((4!/2)) \times F(F(7))) + 3!!))$$

$$34274 := (((3^{F(4)!})/2) + F((7 \times F(4))))$$

$$34275 := (3 + (F((F(4)^2)) \times (7!/5)))$$

$$34277 := (((F(3)!)! + ((F(4)!)!) + (2 - F((F(7) + (7))))))$$

$$34278 := (3!! + (F((4^2)) \times (F(7) + F(8))))$$

$$34280 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 0$$

$$34281 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 1$$

$$34282 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 2$$

$$34283 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 3$$

$$34284 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 4$$

$$34285 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 5$$

$$34286 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 6$$

$$34287 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 7$$

$$34288 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 8$$

$$34289 := F(3!) - F(4!) + 2 \times 8! + 9$$

$$34290 := ((F(F(3!)) - (((F(4)!)!)/(-2))) \times 90)$$

- 34293** := $((F(3!))! - (F(4^2)) + ((9 - F(3)))!)$
34294 := $(((((F(3!))! - (F(4))!) \times 2) - (-F(9) + F(4))))$
34295 := $((((3!! + F(F(4)))/2) \times 95)$
34296 := $((((3!! \times (F(4))!) + ((F(2) - F(9)))) \times F(6))$
34298 := $((F(3!) - F(4!)) + (2 \times (9 + 8!)))$
34299 := $-((F(F(3!)) - ((-F(F(4))) \times (F(-(2 - 9))))!)/(-9!))$
34306 := $(((((F(3!))! - F(4!)) + (F(3!))!) + F((0! + F(6))))$
34307 := $((3!! + F((4! - 3!) + 0!)) \times 7)$
34308 := $((3!^{F(F(4))}) \times (3!! + F(F(-(0! - 8))))))$
34309 := $(((((F(3!))! + ((F(4))!)!) - F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) + F(9))$
34314 := $((((-F(F(3!))) - (F((F(4))!)!) \times (-F(3))) - F(((1 \times 4)!))$
34315 := $(3!! - (((F((F(4))!)!)/(-3!)) + 1) \times 5)$
34319 := $(-F(F(3)) + ((-F(F(4))) \times (F((3! + 1))))!)/(-9!))$
34320 := $((3!!/F(4)) \times (F((3! \times 2)) - 0!))$
34322 := $((((3! + (F(F(4))^{F(3!)}))^2)/2)$
34324 := $(((((F(3!))! + (4! + F(3))) \times 2) - F(4!))$
34325 := $(3!! - (((F((F(4))!)!)/3!) + F(2)) \times (-5))$
34326 := $((3! \times (F(4)^{F(3!)})) - ((F(2) + (6)))!)$
34327 := $((3!! \times (4! \times F(3))) - F((F(2) \times F(7))))$
34333 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4!) - ((33^{F(3)}))))$
34334 := $((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) - (((3^{F(3!)} - F(4!))))$
34335 := $((-3!) + F((4^{F(3)}))) \times 35)$
34336 := $(((((3!! - (F(4))!) \times 3!) + F(3!)) \times F(6))$
34337 := $(F(F(3)) + ((4^{3!}) + (3! \times 7!)))$
34338 := $(-3!) \times (((F(F(4)) - 3!!) \times F(3!)) + (F(8)))$
34339 := $(-((F(F(3)) + F(4!))) + (F(3) \times ((F(3!))! + F(9))))$
34342 := $((-((3!! - F(4!))) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (((F(4))!)!)/(-2))$
34343 := $((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) + ((F(F(3!)) \times (-4!)) + (F(3!))!))$
34345 := $((F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) - (F(3!))!) - ((F(4) \times 5!)))$
34346 := $((((F(F(F(3!))) + F(((F(4))! + F(3!)))) \times 4) - F(F(F(6))))$
34347 := $(F(F(3!)) + (((F(4)^{F(3!)} \times (F(4))!) - (7!)))$
34348 := $(-F(3) + (F(4) \times ((F(F(3!)) \times 4!) + F(F(8))))$
34349 := $((3!! + F(F(4)) - F(F(3!))) \times 49)$
34350 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + (4! \times F(F(3!)))) \times F((5 - 0!)))$

- 34351** := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4!) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-51))))$
34354 := $-((F(F(3!)) - (F((4 + 3!)) \times (5^4))))$
34356 := $(3! \times ((F(4)! - (F(3!) \times (5 - 6!))))$
34357 := $((3! \times (((F(4)! \times F(3!)) + (5))) - F(F(7)))$
34360 := $(F(3!) \times (- (4! - ((3! \times 6!) - 0!)))$
34362 := $(3! \times (((4 - 3!!) \times (-F(6))) - F(2)))$
34363 := $(-(((3!! - F(4!))/F(3!))) + F((F(F(6)) + F(3))))$
34364 := $((F(3!) \times (- (4! - (3! \times 6!)))) - 4$
34366 := $-((F(3) + ((4! - (3! \times 6!)) \times F(6)))$
34367 := $((((F(3!) + F(4!))/F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7)))$
34369 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4)^{F(3!)} - (F((6 + 9))))$
34370 := $((F(3!)^{F(4)} - F(F(3!))) \times 70$
34372 := $((((F(3!))! + F((4! - F(F(3)))))) - F(F(7)))/2$
34373 := $(F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))) - ((F(3!) - (7!)) \times 3!))$
34374 := $((((3!! - F(4)) \times F(3!)) - 7) \times (F(4)!))$
34375 := $((F(3!) + F(4)) \times (-((F(3) - (7)))^5))$
34376 := $((((3!! - (F(4)!)) \times 3!) + F(7)) \times F(6))$
34378 := $((F(3!))! - (((F(4)!^{F(3)} - (7!)) + F(F(8))))$
34379 := $((((F(3!))! - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(3!)))) + ((7! - F(9))))$
34382 := $((3!! \times 4!) - F((3 + 8))) \times 2$
34383 := $((((F(3!)^{F(4)} + 3) + F(F(8))) \times 3$
34384 := $((((3!! \times (F(4)!)) - F(F(3))) - (F(8))) \times F((F(4)!))$
34386 := $(- (3!) + (((F(4)! \times 3!!) - (F(8))) \times F(6)))$
34387 := $((F(3!))! - (((4! + 3) + F(F(8))) - (7!)))$
34388 := $((F(3!))! - (4 - ((3!! + (F(8))) \times (-8))))$
34389 := $((- (3!) \times F((4^{F(3)}))) + ((8! - 9)))$
34392 := $(F(3!) \times (((F(4)! \times 3!!) - F((9 - F(2))))$
34393 := $((- (F((- (3) + 4!))) - F(F(3!))) - (- (9!)/F(3!)))$
34394 := $((- ((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (- (9!)/F((F(4)!)))$
34395 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F(3!)) + (9 + 5!)))$
34396 := $((F(3) - ((4 + 3)!) \times (-9)) - F(F(F(6))))$
34397 := $((F(3!))! - F(F(F(4))) - ((3! \times F((9 + 7))))$
34398 := $((3! + ((4! \times F(3)) \times F(9))) \times F(8))$
34399 := $((F((F(F(3)) + (4!))) - (F(3!))! - (9 \times F(9)))$

- 34404** := $((F(3!))! - ((F((4 \times 4)) - 0!) \times (F(4))!))$
34405 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F((F(4))!)) - (0! - 5!)))$
34406 := $(((((F(3!))! - F((F(4))!)) + (((F(4))! + 0!))!) - F(F(F(6))))$
34407 := $((F(F(3!)))^4 + F(4!))/07$
34408 := $(((((3!! - F(4)) \times (F(4))!) - 0!) \times 8)$
34412 := $-(((F(F(F(3!))) - (F((F(4))!))!) - (((((F(4))! + 1))! - 2))))$
34413 := $((F(3) \times (4!^{F(4)})) + F((-1 + F(F(3!))))$
34414 := $(((((3!! - F(4)) \times 4!) - 1) \times F(F(4)))$
34416 := $((F(3) \times 4!) \times (-((4 - 1) + 6!))$
34417 := $((((3!! - F(4)) + F((4! + 1))) + (7!))$
34418 := $(((((F(3!))! + 4) + (((F(4))! + 1))!) - F(F(8)))$
34422 := $((F(F(3!)) - (4! \times (((F(4))! - 2))) \times (-2))$
34423 := $((F(3!) \times ((F(4))!)) + ((F(4))! + (F(23))))$
34424 := $(((((3!! - F(4)) \times (F(4))!) + F(2)) \times F((F(4))!))$
34427 := $(F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))) - ((F(4))! \times (-F(2) + 7!)))$
34428 := $(3! \times (((F(4))!)) \times F((F(4))!) - (F(2) + F(8)))$
34433 := $((F(3!))! - F(F(F(4)))) - (((F(4!) + 3!!)/F(3!)))$
34434 := $((F(3!))! + (-((F((4 \times 4)) - 3!)) \times (F(4))!))$
34435 := $-(((F((F(3)^4)) - F(4!)) + F(F((3 + 5))))$
34436 := $((F(3!))! + (F(F(4)) + ((F(4!) + 3!!)/(-F(6))))$
34437 := $((3!! + ((F(4!)/4!) - 3)) \times F(7))$
34438 := $((((3 + F(4!)) - F((4^{F(3)}))) - F(F(8)))$
34439 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) + (F(4)^{F(3!)}))/9))$
34441 := $((F(3!) \times ((F(4))!)) - (-4! - F((4! - 1)))$
34442 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (-4! \times (F((F(4))!) - (F((4^2))))))$
34443 := $((3!! + ((F(4)^4))) \times 43$
34444 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + F(4)) \times F(4) + F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 4)))$
34446 := $((F(3!) - (F((4 \times 4)))) \times (F(4))! + (F(6))!)$
34447 := $(((((F(F(3!)) - 4)^{F(4)} + F((F(4))!)) \times 7)$
34448 := $(((((3!! - F(4)) \times (F(4))!) + 4) \times 8)$
34449 := $(((((F(3!))! + F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(4))!)) - (F(4!)/9))$
34452 := $((-((3!! - 4!)) \times (F(F((F(4))!) - 5!)))/2)$
34453 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (F(4!)/(-4!)) + (F((5^{F(3)})))$
34454 := $(((((3!! - F(F(4))) \times 4!) - (5)) \times F(F(4)))$

- 34455** := (((3! + F((4! - (4)))) + 5!) × 5)
34456 := (((3!! - F(4)) × (F(4))!) + (5)) × F(6))
34457 := ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)}) + (-4) - (-5 × 7!))
34458 := -((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4!) - (4 + (5! × 8))))
34459 := -((F(F(F(3!))) - (((F(4) + (4)))! + (5)) × 9))
34462 := -((F(3) - ((4! + 4!) × (6! - 2)))
34463 := (((3!! - F(F(4))) × (F(4))!) × F(6)) - F(F(3)))
34464 := (F(3) × (4! - ((F(4) - 6!) × 4!))
34465 := (((F(3!))! / (-F(F(4)))) + ((F(F((F(4))!)) - F(F(F(6)))) × (-5)))
34466 := (F(3) + (4! × ((-4) + 6!) + 6!))
34467 := (((F((3 + 4))⁴) + F(F(F(6)))) - (7!))
34468 := -((((F(3!))! / ((F(4))!)) - ((F(4!) / (-F(6))) + 8!))
34469 := ((-((F((F(3)⁴) - F(4!))) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(9))
34470 := ((3!! / F((F(4))!)) × ((F(4))! + F((F(7) + 0!))))
34471 := ((-((F(3!))! + F((F(F(F(4))) + (4!)))) - ((F(F(7)) + 1)))
34472 := -((F(3!) × ((F(4)^{F(4)!}) - (7! - 2)))
34473 := (((3!! - (F(4!) / (-4!))) × F(7)) - 3)
34474 := (((3!! - (F(4!) / (-4!))) × F(7)) - F(F(4)))
34478 := (((F(3!)⁴) + F(4!)) - (7!)) - F(F(8))
34479 := -(((F(3!) × ((F(4)^{F(4)!}) - (7!))) + 9))
34482 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) / F((F(4))!)) + (F(8) × 2)))
34483 := ((F(3!))! - ((-4) + (F(4)⁸)) - 3!))
34484 := -((((3! × F(4))^{F(4)}) - 8!) + (4))
34485 := (((3!! + F(4!)) / F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) - (5))
34486 := (((-((3!^{F(4)})) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) - (6!))
34488 := (((3 × F(4))^{F(4)}) × (-8)) + 8!)
34489 := (((F(3!))! - F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(4!) / 8) + F(9)))
34490 := (((3!! + F(4!)) / F(F(4))) + F(F((9 - 0!))))
34491 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) / F((F(4))!)) + (F(9) - 1)))
34492 := ((3!! × (4! + 4!)) + (F(9) × (-2)))
34493 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) / F((F(4))!)) + (F(9) - 3)))
34494 := (((3!! × 4!) - (4! + 9)) × F(F(4)))
34495 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) / F((F(4))!)) + (F(9) - (5))))
34496 := (((F(3!)⁴) - (4! × (-9))) × F(6))

- 34498** := $-(((3!! - F(4!)) + (((F(4))! \times F(9)) + F(F(8))))$
34499 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F((F(4))!)) + (F(9) - 9)))$
34503 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F((5 + 0!)))) - F(F(3!)))$
34509 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!) + 5!)/(- (0! - 9))))$
34512 := $((F(3) \times 4!) \times (((5 + 1))! - F(2)))$
34514 := $((F(3) \times ((F((F(4))!))! + ((5! + 1)))) - F(4!))$
34516 := $-((F(3!) - ((F(4!)/(-F((5 + 1)))) + (F(6))!))$
34517 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F((5 + 1))) + 7))$
34518 := $(F(3) \times ((4! \times ((5 + 1))!) - F(8)))$
34520 := $((3!! \times (F(4))! - 5) \times F(((2 + 0!))!))$
34522 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F(((5 - 2))!)) + 2))$
34523 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(4!)/F(((5 - 2))!)) + F(F(3))))$
34524 := $(((-3) + (4! \times 5!)) \times 2) \times (F(4))!$
34526 := $(F(3) - ((F(4!)/F(((5 - 2))!)) - (F(6))!))$
34528 := $((3!! \times (F(4))! - (5 - F(2))) \times 8)$
- 34530** := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 0$
34531 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 1$
34532 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 2$
34533 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 3$
34534 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 4$
34535 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 5$
34536 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 6$
34537 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 7$
34538 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 8$
34539 := $(F(3!) \times F(4)!! - 5) \times 3! + 9$
- 34540** := $((F(3!))! - (((F(4!) - 5!)/F((F(4))!)) - 0!))$
34541 := $((3!! - 4) - (-5) \times F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 1))))$
34542 := $-((3! \times (F(4) + ((5! \times 4!) \times (-2))))$
34543 := $((F(3!))! - (-4 - ((5! - F(4!))/F(3!))))$
34546 := $(-F(3)) \times (F(F(4)) - (-5) + (4! \times 6!))$
34547 := $((((-3) \times 4!) \times 5!) \times (-4)) - F(7)$
34548 := $((F(F(3)) - ((4! \times 5!)) \times (-4 + 8))$
34549 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - (((F((F(4))!))! + 5!)/(-F((F(4))!))) \times (-9))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 34552 &:= -((F(3!) - ((4! + 5!) \times 5!) \times 2)) \\ 34553 &:= ((3!! - (F((4 \times 5)) \times (-5))) + F(3!)) \\ 34554 &:= (F(3) \times ((4! + 5!) \times 5!) - F(4)) \\ 34555 &:= ((F(3) \times ((4! + 5!) \times 5!)) - (5)) \\ 34556 &:= (-F(3)) \times (F(F(4)) + ((5!/(-5)) \times 6!)) \\ 34558 &:= -((F(3) + ((4! \times (5! + 5!)) - 8!)) \\ 34559 &:= -((F(F(3)) + ((F(F(4)))^5) \times (5! \times (-9)))) \\ 34570 &:= (((F(3!))! / (-F(F(4)))) - (-5 \times F(F((7 + 0!)))) \\ 34572 &:= ((F(F(3)) + ((4! \times 5!)) \times (F(7) - F(2))) \\ 34573 &:= (((F(3!))! - ((F(4!))!) + ((5 - 7!) + F(3!))) \\ 34574 &:= (((F((3 \times 4)) \times 5!) + (7)) \times F(F(4))) \\ 34575 &:= ((3! - (F((F(F((F(4)!)) - (5))) \times (-7))) \times 5) \\ 34576 &:= (F(3!) \times (-((F(4) - (5) - 7!) + 6!)) \\ 34577 &:= ((3! \times (((F(4!))! + (5 + 7!))) - F(7)) \\ 34578 &:= ((3! \times (F(4) - 5!)) - (7! - 8!)) \\ 34581 &:= -((((3!! - F(4!)) + 5!) + F(F(8))) + 1) \\ 34582 &:= (((3!! - F(4!)) + 5!) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(2)) \\ 34583 &:= (((F(F(3)) + F(4!)) - 5!) - F(F(8))) - 3!! \\ 34584 &:= (((F(3) \times ((4 + 5)!)/F(8)) + 4!) \\ 34585 &:= (3!! + ((F((4 \times 5)) + 8) \times 5)) \\ 34586 &:= ((-3!!) \times F((F(4)!)) - ((-5 - 8!) - F(F(6)))) \\ 34587 &:= (((((3 + 4)! - 5!) + F(8)) \times 7) \\ 34589 &:= ((-3!!) \times F((F(4)!)) - ((5 - 8!) - F(9))) \\ 34592 &:= (F(3!) \times (-4) \times ((5! \times (-9)) - F(2))) \\ 34594 &:= (((F(3!))! - ((F(F(4)) + (5)))! + F(9)) - ((F(4!))!)) \\ 34595 &:= ((F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))))) + (5! + F(9))) \times 5) \\ 34596 &:= ((3 + (4! \times 5!)) \times (-9) + F(F(6))) \\ 34597 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 9) + F(F(7)))) \\ 34598 &:= (F(3) \times ((4! - (5)) + (9!/F(8)))) \\ 34600 &:= (F(3!) \times (((F(4!))! \times (6! + 0!)) - 0!)) \\ 34604 &:= (((F(3) \times 4!) \times (6! + 0!)) - (4)) \\ 34606 &:= (-F(3)) + ((F(4!))! \times ((6! + 0!) \times F(6))) \\ 34608 &:= ((F(3) + (4)) \times ((6! + 0!) \times 8)) \\ 34610 &:= (F(3) \times ((4! \times (6! + 1)) + 0!)) \\ 34612 &:= (F(3) \times ((4! \times (6! + 1)) + 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34613 &:= (((3!! - F(4!))/F(6)) - 1) + (F(3!))! \\ 34614 &:= (F(3) \times (F(4) + ((6! + 1) \times 4!))) \\ 34616 &:= (((F(3) \times 4!) \times (6! + 1)) + F(6)) \\ 34623 &:= (((3!! \times 4!) + F(F(6))) \times 2) + F(F(3!)) \\ 34624 &:= ((F(3)^{F(4)!}) - ((6! \times (-2)) \times 4!)) \\ 34626 &:= (3! \times (F(4) + ((6! + F(2)) \times F(6)))) \\ 34627 &:= (((3! \times F((4 + F(F(6)))))) + F(2))/F(7) \\ 34628 &:= (F(3) \times ((4! \times 6!) + F((F(2) + 8)))) \\ 34633 &:= (F(F(3)) + (4! \times ((6! \times F(3)) + 3))) \\ 34634 &:= (F(3) + (4! \times ((6! \times F(3)) + F(4)))) \\ 34635 &:= (((3! \times F(4!))/F(6)) - F(F(3!))) - 5! \\ 34636 &:= ((F(3) - (-4!) \times F((F(6) \times F(3)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 34637 &:= (((3!! \times (F(4)!)) + F(6)) \times F(3!)) + F(7) \\ 34638 &:= -((3! \times (F(4) + ((6! + F(3)) \times (-8)))) \\ 34640 &:= (F(3) \times ((4! \times 6!) + 40)) \\ 34641 &:= -((((F(3)^{F(4)!}) + (F(6)!)) - F((4! + 1)))) \\ 34642 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times (-F(4))) - (((F(6)! - F((4! + F(2)))))) \\ 34644 &:= (((3!! + F(F(4))) \times F(6)) - F(F(4))) \times (F(4)! \\ 34645 &:= (((F(3!))! - (F(4!)/F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) + 5! \\ 34646 &:= (-((3!! - F(4!))) - (((F(6)!/(F(4)!))! + F(F(F(6)))))) \\ 34647 &:= ((-(3^4) + (F(6)!)) + (-4! \times F(F(7)))) \\ 34648 &:= (((3!! \times (F(4)!)) + (F(6) + F(4))) \times 8) \\ 34649 &:= (F(F(3!)) + (F(F(4)) \times ((6! \times 4!) + F(9)))) \\ 34651 &:= ((-(3!! - F(4!))) - F(F(F(6)))) - 51 \\ 34653 &:= (((3! \times F(4!))/F(6)) - ((5! + 3))) \\ 34654 &:= (((3! \times F(4!))/F(6)) - 5!) - F(F(4)) \\ 34656 &:= -((3! \times (((F(4) - 6!) - 5) \times F(6))) \\ 34657 &:= (((3 + 4)! - F((6 + 5))) \times 7) \\ 34660 &:= (-3!!) + (F(F(4)) \times (-F(F(6))) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!)))) \\ 34662 &:= ((F((3 + 4!)) \times 6)/F((F(6) + F(2)))) \\ 34663 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) - (((F(6)! + (F(F(6)) \times F(3)))))) \\ 34664 &:= (F(3!) + (((4 + 6!) + 6!) \times 4!)) \\ 34665 &:= (((F(3) \times 4!) \times 6!) - (F(F(6)) \times (-5))) \\ 34666 &:= ((-(3!! - F(4!))) - F(F(F(6)))) - (6 \times 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$34667 := (((3!! + F(4!)) / (-F(6))) + (F(6))! + F(F(7)))$$

$$34669 := (((F(F(3)) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (6! + F(9)))$$

$$34670 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 0$$

$$34671 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 1$$

$$34672 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 2$$

$$34673 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 3$$

$$34674 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 4$$

$$34675 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 5$$

$$34676 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 6$$

$$34677 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 7$$

$$34678 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 8$$

$$34679 := F(3)! - F(-F(4)! + F(F(6))) - 7! + 9$$

$$34680 := -((((3!! - F(4!)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) + 0!))$$

$$34681 := (((3!! - F(4!)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times (-1)$$

$$34682 := -((((3!! - F(4!)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) - F(2))$$

$$34683 := ((((-3!) \times F(4!)) + (6!)) / (-8)) - 3$$

$$34684 := ((F(F(3)) - (4!)) \times (F((6 + 8)) \times (-4)))$$

$$34685 := (-3) - (((F((F(4)!))!)/(-F(F(6)))) - (8^5))$$

$$34686 := (((F(3)^{F(4)}) \times 6!) + F(8)) \times 6$$

$$34687 := ((((-F(3)) + F(4!)) - (6!)) - F(F(8))) - F(7)$$

$$34688 := (((F(3)^4) - 6!) \times 8) + 8!$$

$$34689 := -((((3!! - F(4!)) - F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) + F(9))$$

$$34692 := ((F(3)! - (F(4) \times (6! + (F(9)^2))))$$

$$34693 := (F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) - (((F(6))! + (9 + 3))))$$

$$34694 := (F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) - (((F(6))! + 9) + F(F(4))))$$

$$34696 := (((3!! \times (F(4)!)) + (F(6) + 9)) \times F(6))$$

$$34697 := -((((F(3)! + F((F(4)!)) - F((F(F(6)) + (-9) + F(7))))))$$

$$34698 := (3! \times ((F(4!)/F(6)) - (F(9) - F(8))))$$

$$34699 := (((-3) - F(4)) - (F(6))! + F((F(9) - 9)))$$

$$34701 := ((-(3!! - F(4!))) - F(F((7 + 0!)))) - 1$$

$$34702 := -(((3!! - F(4!)) + F((7 \times (0! + 2))))$$

$$34703 := ((F(3)! - (4! \times (F(F(7)) + 0!)) + F(F(3))))$$

$$34704 := ((3!! + F(4)) \times ((F(7) - 0!) \times 4))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34705 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + (4!))) - ((F(7) + (0 - 5))))! \\
 34706 &:= ((F(F(3)) + F((4! + ((7 \times 0)!))) - (F(6)))! \\
 34707 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + F((0! + (7)))))) \\
 34708 &:= ((3 + F((4! + ((7 \times 0)!))) - 8!) \\
 34709 &:= (-(((3! - F(4!)) - 7) - F(F(-(0! - 9)))))) \\
 34711 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4!) - 711))) \\
 34712 &:= ((F((F(F(3)) + (4!))) + 7) - (F(((1 + 2)!)))! \\
 34714 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + 14)) \\
 34715 &:= (-(((3! - F(4!)) - F(7)) - F(F(F((1 + 5)))))) \\
 34716 &:= (-(((3! - F(4!)) - (F(7) + 1))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 34718 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + (4!))) + (F(7) - ((1 \times 8)!)) \\
 34719 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + (1 \times 9))) \\
 34720 &:= (((F(3)! + (-4!) \times F(F(7))) - F((2 + 0)!))! \\
 34722 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + (F((2 + 2)!)))! \\
 34723 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + (2 + 3))) \\
 34724 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + (F(2) + F(4)))) \\
 34725 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - ((2 - 5)))) \\
 34726 &:= -((F(3) - (4! \times (7 + (2 \times 6!)))))) \\
 34728 &:= (((3! \times (-4)) \times F(F(7))) + ((F(2) \times 8!)) \\
 34729 &:= ((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - (F(2)^9))) \\
 \\
 34730 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 0 \\
 34731 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 1 \\
 34732 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 2 \\
 34733 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 3 \\
 34734 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 4 \\
 34735 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 5 \\
 34736 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 6 \\
 34737 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 7 \\
 34738 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 8 \\
 34739 &:= F(3)! - 4! \times F(F(7)) + F(3)! + 9 \\
 \\
 34740 &:= ((3!/4) \times (F(F(7)) - 40)) \\
 34741 &:= (((F(3)! + (-4!) \times F(F(7))) + F(((F(4)! + 1))) \\
 34743 &:= (((F(3)! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) + (F(4)!)) + F(F(3!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34744 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - (4 \times 4))) \\ 34745 &:= (((F(3!))! / (F(4))!) + (F(F(7)) - 4)) \times 5 \\ 34746 &:= (3! \times (((-4!) - F(F(7))) + F(4!)) - (F(6))!) \\ 34747 &:= -(((F(3!)^{F(4)}) - ((7! - F(4)) \times 7)) \\ 34748 &:= ((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(F(7)) \times (-4!)) + 8!)) \\ 34749 &:= (((3^4) \times F(7)) \times (4! + 9)) \\ 34753 &:= ((F(3!) \times ((F(4))! - (7!))) + F((5^{F(3)}))) \\ 34754 &:= ((3^{F(F(4)!)} + (F(F(7)) \times (5! + F(F(F(4)))))) \\ 34757 &:= ((F((3! \times F(4))) \times F(7)) + (5 \times F(F(7)))) \\ 34758 &:= (((3! \times F(4!)) - (F((7 + 5)))) / 8) \\ 34759 &:= (F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(F(7)) \times 5!) + F(9))) \\ 34760 &:= (F(3!) \times (((4! + 7!) - 6!) + 0!)) \\ 34762 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - F((F(6) + F(2)))) \\ 34763 &:= (((3! \times F(4!)) - ((F(7) \times F(6)))) / F(3!)) \\ 34764 &:= (((34 + 7!) + 6!) \times (F(4))!) \\ 34765 &:= (((F(3!))! / (F(4))!) + F((7 + 6))) \times 5 \\ 34766 &:= ((-F(3)) - ((F(4!) - F(7)) \times (-6))) / F(6) \\ 34767 &:= (F(3!) + (((F(4))!^7) / F(6)) - F(F(7))) \\ 34768 &:= (((F(3) + 4!) + 7!) - 6!) \times 8 \\ 34770 &:= (3! \times ((F(4!) / F((-7) + F(7))) - 0!)) \\ 34774 &:= (((3 \times F(4!)) - F((-7) + F(7))) / 4) \\ 34775 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (4!)) \times (-F(7) \times (F(7) - 5!))) \\ 34778 &:= (F(3) - ((F(4!) \times (7 - F(7))) / 8)) \\ 34782 &:= (3! \times ((F(4!) / (-F(7) - F(8))) + F(2))) \\ 34783 &:= (((3! \times F(4!)) + ((7 \times 8))) / F(3!)) \\ 34784 &:= (F(3!) + (((F(4!) / (-7)) \times F(8)) / (-4))) \\ 34786 &:= (((-3!) + F(4!)) + (7! / (-8))) - F(F(F(6))) \\ 34787 &:= -((((3!! + (F(4))!) - F(F(7))) - (8! - 7!)) \\ 34790 &:= ((F((F(3)^4)) + 7) \times (F(9) + 0!)) \\ 34792 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4!) - (7! / (9 - F(2)))))) \\ 34793 &:= ((-3!!) \times F((F(4))!)) + ((F(F(7)) + (F((9 - 3))))!) \\ 34794 &:= (-3) \times ((F(4) - 7!) - (9^4)) \\ 34797 &:= (3 \times ((F(4!) / (F(7) - 9)) + 7)) \\ 34798 &:= ((-3!!) \times F((F(4))!)) - ((-7) \times F(9)) - 8!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34803 &:= (3 \times ((F(4)^8) + ((0! + 3!)!)) \\ 34806 &:= (3! \times ((F(4!)/8) - ((0! - (6)))) \\ 34809 &:= (((3! \times F(4!))/8) - ((0! - F(9)))) \\ 34812 &:= (((3!! \times 4) + (F(8))) \times 12) \\ 34813 &:= ((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) - (- (8!) + F((1 + F(3!)))) \\ 34815 &:= (((3 + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) - (F(15))) \\ 34818 &:= (3! \times ((F(4!)/8) - ((1 - 8))) \\ 34822 &:= ((F(3!))! - (4! - ((F(F(8)))/(-2)) - F(2))) \\ 34823 &:= ((F(3!))! - (4! - (F(F(8)))/(F(2) - 3))) \\ 34824 &:= (((3! \times F(4!))/8) + (2 \times 4!)) \\ 34825 &:= (((F(3) + F(4)))! - (8! - F(25))) \\ 34826 &:= (((F(3)^{F(4)})! + ((F(F(8)))/(-2)) - F(F(6))) \\ 34827 &:= ((F(F(3!)) + ((F(4!))!)) \times (F(8) + (2 \times F(7))) \\ 34828 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((-4) + F(F(8)))/2) + (F(8))) \\ 34829 &:= ((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) + ((8! - ((2 \times 9)))) \\ 34830 &:= (3! \times (((F(4!)/8) + F(3!)) + 0!)) \\ 34832 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((4! + F(F(8))) + 3!)/2)) \\ 34833 &:= (((F((3! + 4))) - F(F(8))) - 3!) \times (-3) \\ 34834 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((4! + F(F(8))) + F(3))/F(F(4)))) \\ 34835 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4! + F(F(8)))/(- (3 - 5)))) \\ 34836 &:= (((3!! + (F(4)!)) \times 8) - F(3)) \times 6 \\ 34837 &:= (((3!! + 4!) + F(F(8))) \times 3) - F(F(7)) \\ 34838 &:= (((3! \times F(4)) + F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) + 8! \\ 34839 &:= (((3!! + (F(4)!)) \times (8 \times 3!)) - 9) \\ 34840 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(4)! + ((F(F(8)))/F(F(4))) + 0!)) \\ 34841 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(4)! - (F(F(8)))/(-F((4 - 1)))))) \\ 34842 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((4 + F(F(8))) + (F(4)!)/2)) \\ 34843 &:= (((-3) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) - (4!^{F(3)}) \\ 34844 &:= (((-F(3) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) - (4! \times 4!)) \\ 34845 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4 + F(F(8)))/(- (F(4) - (5)))) \\ 34846 &:= ((-F(3) + F(4!)) + ((8 - 4!) \times 6!)) \\ 34847 &:= (((F(3)^{F(4)})! - (F(F(8)))/F(-((4 - 7)))) \\ 34849 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) + (-8!) + F((F(4) + 9))) \\ 34850 &:= (((3!! - F(F(4))) - (F(8))) \times 50) \end{aligned}$$

- 34851 := ((F(3!))! - (-4) + (F(F(8))/F(F((5-1))))))
34852 := ((-F(3)) × (((F(4))!)! - F(F(8)))) + (5!²)
34853 := ((F(3!))! + (((F(4))! - (F(F(8))/(5-3))))))
34854 := ((F(3!) - ((F(4!)/(-8)) - (5))) × (F(4))!)
34856 := ((F(3!) + F(4!)) - (((F(8) - 5) × 6!))
34857 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(4) × (F(8) + 5!) + 7!))
34859 := (F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) - (((8! - 5!) - F(9))))
34860 := ((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) - (-8! - F((F(6) - 0!))))
34862 := ((F(3!))! - (((-4!) + F(F(8))) - 6)/2))
34863 := (((3! - 4!) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) × 3
34864 := (((3! - F(F(F(4)))) × (-8 - F(6))) + F(4!))
34865 := (((3! × F(4!))/8) + (F((6 + 5))))
34866 := (3! × (F(4) + (8 × (6! + (6))))))
34867 := (F(F(F(3!))) + ((4! × F((8 + F(6)))) + F(F(7))))
34868 := ((F(3!))! - (((F(4) × F(F(8)))/6) - (F(8))))
34872 := ((F(3!))! - (-4!) × ((8 - F(F(7))) - 2))
34873 := (F((F(F(3)) + 4!)) + ((F(8) - 7!) × F(3!))
34874 := ((F((F(3)⁴) × (-F(8) + F(F(7))))/(F(4))!)
34877 := ((3! × ((F(4!) - 8!) - F(F(7)))) - F(7))
34878 := ((3 × (((F(4))!)! + F(F(8)))) - ((F(7) - 8))!)
34879 := (F(-((F(3) - 4!)) + (8 - ((F(7))! / (-9!))))
34881 := ((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) + ((8! + F((8 + 1))))))
34883 := (((3!^{F(4)}) + 8!) + (F(F(8))/(-F(3))))
34884 := (3! × ((F(4!)/8) + (F(8) - F(4))))
34889 := ((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) - ((-8) - 8!) - F(9))
34890 := (3! × (((F(4))!)! × 8) + F((9 + 0!)))
34893 := (-3) - (-F(4) × ((F(F(8)) - F(9)) + 3!))
34894 := (((3!^{F(4)}) - F(F(8))) - ((F(9) × 4!))
34896 := (((3! × (F(4))!) + (8 + F(9))) × F(6))
34899 := ((3 × (((F(4))!)! + F(F(8)))) - (99))
34904 := (((3! + (F(4))!) × (F(9) - 0!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
34918 := ((F(F(3!)) × (4! × 91)) - F(F(8)))
34923 := (((F(3!))! / 4!) - (F(9) / 2)) × F(F(3!))
34924 := (3! + (((F((F(4))!)! - F(9)) × 2) - F(4!)))

- 34926** := $(3 \times ((-4!) + F(F((9 - F(2)))))) + (6!))$
34928 := $((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) - ((9^2) - 8!))$
34935 := $((F(3!))! - (F(4!)/9) - F(F((F(3) + (5))))))$
34936 := $((((F(3!) \times F(4!)) + 9!)/F(F(3!))) - F(6))$
34937 := $((F(F(3)) \times 49) \times (3!! - 7))$
34938 := $((F((F(F(3)) + (4!))) + F(F((9 - F(3)))))) - 8!$
34942 := $((((F(3!) \times F(4!)) + 9!)/F(F((F(4)!)))) - 2)$
34943 := $((((F(3!) \times F(4!)) + 9!)/F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(F(3)))$
34944 := $(F(3) \times ((4! \times (9^{F(4)})) - 4!))$
34945 := $((F(F(3)) + F(4!)) - ((-F(9)) \times (F((F(4)!))!)/(-5!)))$
34946 := $((((F(3!) + (F(4)!)) \times (-F(9))) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(6))))$
34947 := $(-3) + (((F(4)! + F((9 + F(4)))) \times F(F(7))))$
34948 := $((F(F(3!)) - ((F(4)!))! \times (-9)) + F((F(F(4)) + (F(8))))))$
34952 := $(-3!!) + (((F(4)!))! - F(9)) \times 52)$
34956 := $(3 \times (((F(4)!))! - (9 + 5)) + F(F(F(6))))$
34957 := $((F(F(3)) - (((F((F(4)!))! - 9!)/5!)) \times F(7))$
34958 := $((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(F(4)))) - ((9 - 5!) - 8!))$
34959 := $((-F(F(3))) - (F((F(4)!)) \times (-F(9)))) \times (5! + 9)$
34962 := $(3 \times ((F((F(4)!))! - (9 + F((F(F(6)) + 2))))))$
34963 := $(-F(3!)) + (((F(4)!))! - 9) + F(F(F(6))) \times 3)$
34964 := $((3!! \times F(4) - F(9)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(4)))$
34965 := $(F(F(3!)) + ((F(4!) + ((-F(9)) \times (F(6)!)/5!))))$
34966 := $((F(3!))! - ((-4!) \times F((F(9) - F(F(6)))))) + F(F(F(6))))$
34967 := $(((((F(3!))! - ((F(4)!))!)/9) \times F(6)) - F(F(7)))$
34969 := $((-F(3)) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times 9))^{F(-6+9)})$
34971 := $(3 \times (((F(4)!))! + (-9) + F(F((7 + 1))))))$
34975 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4!) - ((F(9) \times F(7)) + (5))))))$
34976 := $((3!! + 4!) \times (F(9) + F(7))) + F(6)$
34977 := $((3!!/(-F(4))) + ((-9) + 7!) \times 7)$
34978 := $(((-F(3)) + F(4!)) - ((F(9) \times F(7)))) - F(F(8))$
34979 := $((3 + 4) \times ((-9) + 7!) - F(9))$
34980 := $(3 \times ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(9)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-0!))))$
34981 := $((3 \times ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(9)) + F(F(8)))) + 1)$
34982 := $((3!! \times 4!) - 9) + F((F(8) + F(2)))$

- 34983** := $((3!! - F(4!)) + (-9) + (8! \times F(3)))$
34984 := $-(((3!! \times (F(4))!) - (F(9))^{F(8-4)}))$
34985 := $((3 \times ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(9)) + F(F(8)))) + (5))$
34986 := $((3!! - (F(4))!) \times ((F(9) + F(8)) - (6)))$
34987 := $((F(3!))! - ((F((F(4))!) \times F(9)) + ((F(8) + 7!))))$
34988 := $(F(3!) + (F(4) \times ((F(9) \times F(8)) + F(F(8))))$
34991 := $(F(-(F(3) - 4!)) + ((9!/F((9 - 1))))$
34993 := $(F(F(3)) + ((F(4))! \times ((9 + 9)^3))$
34994 := $(F(3) + ((F(4))! \times ((9 + 9)^{F(4)}))$
34998 := $(3 \times (((4 - (9/9)))!)! + F(F(8)))$
35035 := $-(((F(F(3)) - (50)) \times (3!! - (5))))$
35046 := $(-(3!) \times (((5 + 0!)! - (F(4))^{F(6)}))$
35047 := $((((F(3) + (5)))! \times (0! + (F(4))!)) - F(F(7)))$
35049 := $((F(3!))! + (-((5! - 0!)) - (F(4!)/9))$
35062 := $((-3) \times 5!) - (F((0! + F(F(6)))) \times (-2))$
35064 := $(((F(3) \times ((5 + 0!)!)) + F(F(6))) \times 4!)$
35092 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + (5! \times F((0! + 9)))) \times 2)$
35133 := $(-(F(3) - (51))) \times (3!! - 3)$
35134 := $((((F(3!))! - F(F(F((5 + 1)))))) - (-3!! \times F((F(4))!)))$
35137 := $((((3!!)/(-5)) + 1) + (F(3!))! - (7!))$
35138 := $((((F(3!))! \times (-5 - 1)) + (F((3! + F(8))))))$
35144 := $((F(F(F(3!))) - (((5 + 1)! \times F(4))) \times 4)$
35145 := $(3!! + (((-5!) - F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))))) \times (-5))$
35147 := $((((F(3!))! - 5!) - ((1 + (F(4))!))!) - F(7))$
35152 := $((((F(F(3!)) + (5))^{F(-1+5)})) \times 2)$
35157 := $((-3) + (F((5 + 1)))!) - (5! + 7!))$
- 35160** := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 0$
35161 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 1$
35162 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 2$
35163 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 3$
35164 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 4$
35165 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 5$
35166 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 6$
35167 := $F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 7$

$$35168 := F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 8$$

$$35169 := F(3!)! - 5! - (1 + 6)! + 9$$

$$35174 := (((F(F(3!)) \times (-5)) - (1 + 7!)) + (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$35175 := (F(F(3!)) \times (-5) - ((-1 - F(7)) \times 5!))$$

$$35176 := ((F(F(3!)) \times (-5)) + ((1 - 7!) + (F(6)!))$$

$$35177 := ((F(3!))! - ((5! - (17)) + 7!))$$

$$35178 := (((F(3) \times (-51)) - 7!) + 8!)$$

$$35180 := (F(3) \times (-((5! + 1)) + F((F(8) + 0!))))$$

$$35181 := ((F(3) \times (-5!) + F((1 + F(8)))) - 1)$$

$$35182 := (((F(F(3)) \times 5!) - F((1 + F(8)))) \times (-2))$$

$$35183 := (F(F(3)) + ((5! - F((1 + F(8)))) \times (-F(3))))$$

$$35184 := (((F(F(3)) - 5!) + F((1 + F(8)))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$35187 := (((-F(3)) + F(((5 - 1)!)) - F(F(8))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$35189 := -((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(((5 - 1)!)) - F(-(F(8) - F(9))))))$$

$$35217 := ((F(3!) - (((5 + 2)! - 1)) \times (-7))$$

$$35224 := ((F(3!) - ((5 + 2)! \times (-F(2)) - (F(4)!))$$

$$35225 := ((F(3!))! - (((5 + 2)! + F((2 \times 5))))$$

$$35227 := ((F(3!))! - ((52 + F(2)) + 7!))$$

$$35228 := (((F(3!))! - 52) - (-((F(2) - 8)!))$$

$$35234 := (F(F(F(3!))) - (((((5 - F(2))!)) / (F(F(3!))!)) \times F(F(4))))$$

$$35235 := (((3! / 5) + F(2)) \times (3^5))$$

$$35237 := -((F(F(3)) - (((5 + 2)! - 3!) \times 7))$$

$$35238 := (((3! - ((5 + 2)! / (-3)) \times F(8))$$

$$35240 := ((F(3!))! - (((5 + 2)! + 40))$$

$$35244 := -(((F((3! + 5))) - F((-2 + 4!))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$35245 := ((F(3) + 5) \times (((F(2) + (F(4)!))! - 5))$$

$$35246 := ((F(3!))! - (((5 + 2)! + F((F(4) + (6))))))$$

$$35247 := (((F(3!))! - (5^2)) - F((F(4)!)) - 7!))$$

$$35248 := -((F(3!) + (((5 + 2)! + 4!) - 8!))$$

$$35249 := ((F(3!))! - (((5 + 2)! - F(4)) + F(9)))$$

$$35250 := ((F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 250)$$

$$35254 := (((F(3!))! - (5 + ((2 + 5)!)) - F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$35255 := ((F(3!))! - (((5 + 2)! + ((5 \times 5))))$$

$$35256 := ((-(((F(3) + 5)!)) - (-((F(2) - 5)!)) + (F(6)!))$$

- 35259** := (((F(3!)! - ((5 + 2)!) - F(F((F(-(5 - 9))))!)))
35260 := ((F(3!)! + ((-(((5 + 2)!) - F(F(6))) + 0!))
35264 := (((F(3!) - ((5 + 2)!) + (F(6)!) - (4!))
35265 := ((F(3!)! - ((5 × F((2 × F(6)))) + 5!))
35266 := ((-((3! + ((5 + 2)!)) + (F(6)!) - F(6))
35267 := ((-((3 - 52) × 6!) - F(7))
35269 := ((-((F(3) + ((5 + 2)!)) + (F(6)!) - 9)
35271 := -((F(3) - ((5 + 2) × (7! - 1)))
35273 := (((((3 + 5)!) - F(2)) - 7!) - 3!)
35277 := (-3) + (((-5) - F(2)) + F(7)) × 7!)
35279 := (F(3)!) + (((5 + 2) × 7!) - 9)
35281 := (((3 + 5)!) + F(2)) - ((8 - 1)!)
35282 := (((F(3) - ((5 + 2)!) + 8!) × F(2))
35284 := (F(F(3)) - (((((5 + 2)!) - 8!) - F(4))))
35285 := (F(F(3)) × (-(((5 + 2)!) - 8!) - (5)))
35286 := (3! + (((5 + 2) × 8!) / F(6)))
35288 := (F(F(3)) × (-(((5 + 2)!) - 8) - 8!))
35289 := (F(F(3)) × (-(((5 + 2)!) - 8!) - 9))
35290 := ((F(3!)! - (((((5 + 2)!) - 9) - 0!)))
35293 := ((F(3!)! + (F((5 + 2)) - ((9 - F(3))!))
35294 := ((F(3) + (5)) × ((-((2 - 9)))! + F(F(4))))
35296 := ((F(3!)! + ((-5) - (-((2 - 9)))! + F(F(6))))
35297 := ((F(3!)! + ((F(((5 - 2)!) - (-9) + 7!))))
35298 := -((((F(3) + (5))! + (-((2 × 9)) - 8!))
35301 := -((F(F(F(3!))) + ((5! - F(((3 + 0)!)!)) + 1))
35302 := ((F(F(F(3!))) + (5! - F(((3 + 0)!)!))) × (-F(2))
35303 := (((F(F(3)) - 5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(((0! + 3)!)
35304 := (((F(3) + (5)) × ((3! + 0)!) + (4!))
35305 := (((3 - 5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) + F((-((0! - (5))))!)
35306 := ((F(3!)! - ((-5) + ((3! + 0)!) - F(F(6))))
35307 := -((F(3!) - ((-5) - ((3! + 0)!) × (-7)))
35308 := ((3! - 5!) + (F(3) × F((0! + F(8))))
35309 := ((F(3!)! - ((5 + ((3! + 0)!) - F(9)))
35312 := ((F((F(3) × 5)) - F((F(F(3!)) + 1))) × (-2))
35314 := (((F(3!)! - (((5 + F(3))!)) + F((1 + F((F(4)!))))

$$\begin{aligned} 35315 &:= ((F(3) + (5)) \times (((3! + 1)!) + (5))) \\ 35317 &:= (F(3) + ((5 + ((3! + 1)!) \times 7)) \\ 35319 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((-5) + ((3! + 1)!) - F(9))) \\ 35322 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (((5! + 3!!) + F(2)) \times 2)) \\ 35323 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - 5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(((F(2) + 3)!)!))) \\ 35324 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - 5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (-F(2) - F(4!))) \\ 35325 &:= -(((F(3!))! - ((5! + 3)^2) \times 5)) \\ 35327 &:= (((F(3!))! + (5)) + ((F(F(3!)) \times 2) - (7!))) \\ 35332 &:= ((F(F((3 + 5))) + ((F(3!))!/3!)) \times 2) \\ 35333 &:= (((F(3!))! + 53) - ((F(F(3)) + 3!))!) \\ 35334 &:= ((-F((3! + (5)))) - F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(F(3)) + F(4!)))) \\ 35335 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((5 + F(3))!) - F((F(3) \times 5)))) \\ 35336 &:= ((F(3!) + ((5 + F(3))!) \times (F(F(3)) + 6)) \\ 35337 &:= (F(F(3)) - (((5 + F(3))! + F(3!)) \times (-7))) \\ 35338 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - ((5 \times (F(F(3!))³)) - F(F(8)))) \\ 35340 &:= (((F(3!))! + (5!/F(3))) - (((F(4))! + 0!)!)) \\ 35342 &:= (F(3) \times ((5!/(-3)) + F((4! - 2)))) \\ 35343 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (((5 + 3)!)!/4! + 3)) \\ 35344 &:= (((F(3)⁵) \times 3! - (4))^{F(F(4))}) \\ 35345 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F((-5) + F(F(3!)))) + F((F(4)!) \times 5)) \\ 35346 &:= ((F(3) \times (5^{3!})) + (4⁶)) \\ 35347 &:= ((F(3!))! - (5 + ((-3) \times 4!) + 7!)) \\ 35348 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - ((-53) + F(4!) - F(F(8)))) \\ 35349 &:= (((F(3!)⁵) - 3) + F((F(F(4)) \times 9))) \\ 35350 &:= ((3! - F((5 + F(3)))) \times 50) \\ 35352 &:= ((F(3!)⁵) + F((3 \times ((5 - 2)!)!)) \\ 35357 &:= ((F(3) + (5)) \times ((3! + (5)) + 7!)) \\ 35358 &:= ((3 \times F(F((5 + 3)))) + (5! \times F(8))) \\ 35359 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (5 \times (F(F(3!))^{F(-5+9)})))) \\ 35361 &:= (3 \times (((5! + 3!!) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1)) \\ 35362 &:= (((3! \times (-5)) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))))) \times 2) \\ 35364 &:= (((3! + ((5! + F(3)))) \times F(F(6))) \times F(F(4))) \\ 35366 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times 5!) + ((3 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(6))) \\ 35367 &:= (((-F(3)) + F((5 + 3!))) + (F(6)!) - (7!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 35368** := (((F(3) × 5!) + F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) × 8)
35370 := ((F(3!))! + ((F((5 + 3!)) - (7! - 0!)))
35373 := (((F(3!))! + 5!) - F(F(3!))) - ((7! + 3!))
35374 := (F(3) × (F((5 × 3) + 7)) - 4!)
35375 := ((F(3!))! - (((5^{F(3)}) + 7!) - 5!))
35376 := (F(3!) × (-((F((5 × 3)) - 7!) + F(6))))
35377 := (3! + ((5 + F(3)) × (7! + F(7))))
35378 := ((F(3) + (5)) × ((3! + 7!) + 8))
35379 := (((3!! - 5!) + F((F(F(3!)) + 7)))/9)
35380 := (F(3) × (-F((5 + 3))) + F((F(8) + 0!)))
35382 := (F(3) × (-((5!/3!)) + F((F(8) + F(2))))
35383 := ((F(3!))! - ((5 × F((F(3) × 8))) + F(3)))
35384 := ((-((35 + 3)) - F(F(8))) + F(4!))
35385 := (((3!⁵) - 3!!) + (F(8))) × 5)
35386 := (F(F(3)) + ((-5) × F((F(3) × 8))) + (F(6)!))
35387 := ((F(3!))! - ((-5!) - F(3!)) + ((F(8) + 7!)))
35388 := (3 + ((-5) × F((F(3) × 8))) + 8!))
35389 := ((F(F(3)) + F((5 - F(F(3))))!) - (F(F(8)) + F(9)))
35392 := ((F(3!))! - ((-5!) + F(3!)) + ((9 - 2)!))
35393 := -((((F(F(3!)) × F(F((5 + F(3)))))) + F(9)) - (F(3!))!)
35394 := (((3! - F(F((5 + 3)))) - F(9)) + F(4!))
35395 := (((F(3!))! - (5)) - (-((F(3) - 9)))! + 5!)
35396 := (((3! × (-5)) - (3!! × (-F(9)))) + F(F(F(6))))
35397 := ((-3) + 5!) - ((F(3) - 9) × 7!)
35398 := ((-((F(3) - 5!)) - (-((F(3) - 9)))! + 8!)

35400 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 0
35401 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 1
35402 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 2
35403 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 3
35404 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 4
35405 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 5
35406 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 6
35407 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 7
35408 := F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 8

- 35409 := $F(3!)! + 5! - (F(4!) + 0!)! + 9$
- 35410 := $(F(3) \times ((-5) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 1))) - 0!))$
- 35411 := $-(((F(F((3 + 5))) - F(4!)) + 11))$
- 35412 := $(F(3) \times (-5) + F((4! - (1 \times 2))))$
- 35413 := $-((((F(F((3 + 5))) - F(4!)) + 1) + F(3!)))$
- 35414 := $-(((F(3!) - (F((5 \times 4)))) - F((-1 + 4!)))$
- 35415 := $((-((F(3) + (5))) + F(4!)) - F(F(F((1 + 5))))))$
- 35416 := $((F(3!) + (5! + 4!)) \times F(F((1 + 6))))$
- 35417 := $((((F(F(3)) \times (-5)) + F(4!)) - F(F((1 + 7))))$
- 35418 := $((((F(F(3)) - (5)) + F(4!)) - F(F((1 \times 8))))$
- 35419 := $-(((3!! - ((5 + F(4)))!) + (F(19))))$
- 35420 := $(F(3) \times (F((5 \times 4) + 2)) - 0!)$
- 35425 := $((3!! - ((5 + F(4)))!) + F(25))$
- 35426 := $((3!! \times F((5 + 4))) + F(F((2 + 6))))$
- 35427 := $((F(3) + (5)) \times (F((4 \times 2)) + 7!))$
- 35428 := $((3! + F((5 \times 4))) + F((2 + F(8))))$
- 35429 := $-(((F(F((3 + 5))) - F(4!)) + ((2 - 9))))$
-
- 35430 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 0$
- 35431 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 1$
- 35432 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 2$
- 35433 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 3$
- 35434 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 4$
- 35435 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 5$
- 35436 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 6$
- 35437 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 7$
- 35438 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 8$
- 35439 := $-F(F(3 + 5)) + F(4!) + F(3!) + 9$
-
- 35440 := $F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4!)) + 0$
- 35441 := $F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4!)) + 1$
- 35442 := $F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4!)) + 2$
- 35443 := $F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4!)) + 3$
- 35444 := $F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4!)) + 4$
- 35445 := $F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4!)) + 5$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35446 &:= F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 \\
 35447 &:= F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 \\
 35448 &:= F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 \\
 35449 &:= F(3!)! - F(5 \times F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 \\
 \\
 35450 &:= (((3!! - 5)) - (F(4)!) \times 50) \\
 35451 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((5 + 4!) + F(((5 - 1)!)))) \\
 35452 &:= (((3! \times 5) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(((5 - 2)!)))) \\
 35453 &:= (-(((F((3! + 5))) - F(4!)) - 5!)) - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 35454 &:= -((F(F((3 + 5))) - ((F(F(4))^5) + F(4!))) \\
 35456 &:= ((F(3!)^5) + (4! \times (5! - F(6)))) \\
 35457 &:= -(((F(F((3 + 5))) - F(4!)) - (5 \times 7))) \\
 35459 &:= (((3!! - 5!) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 59) \\
 35460 &:= (F(3) \times ((-5) + 4!) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!))) \\
 35461 &:= (((F(3!) \times 5) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - 1) \\
 35462 &:= (((F(3!) \times 5) + F(4!)) - F(F((6 + 2)))) \\
 35463 &:= (((35 + F(4!)) - F(F(F(6)))) + 3!) \\
 35466 &:= (3!! + ((-5) + (F(4!)/F(6))) \times 6) \\
 35467 &:= ((F(3!)! - (5 - ((4! \times F(6)) - 7!))) \\
 35468 &:= (((F(3!) \times 5) + F(4!)) + 6) - F(F(8)) \\
 35469 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times ((5! \times ((F(4)!) + F(6))) + 9)) \\
 35471 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((5! + F(4!)) - (71))) \\
 35472 &:= ((F(3!)^5) + ((4 \times F(7))^2)) \\
 35473 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((-5) + F(4!)) + (7 \times F(3!)))) \\
 35474 &:= (((3!! + 5!) - F(F(4))) \times (-F(7))) + F(4!) \\
 35475 &:= (F((F(3) \times 5)) \times (((F(4)!)! - (75))) \\
 35476 &:= ((F(3!) \times 5) + ((F(4)!) \times (-7!) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 35477 &:= -((((3! - 5!) \times 4!) + (7)) \times F(7)) \\
 35478 &:= (3 \times ((F((5 \times 4)) + 7!) + F(8))) \\
 35479 &:= (((F(3!)! - ((5 + F(F(4))))!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9))) \\
 35480 &:= (F(3) \times ((5 + 4!) + F((F(8) + 0!)))) \\
 35482 &:= (F(3) \times ((5!/4) + F((F(8) + F(2)))))) \\
 35483 &:= (((F((F(3) \times 5)) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) + 3!) \\
 35484 &:= (((F(3!) + 54) - F(F(8))) + F(4!)) \\
 35486 &:= -(((F(F((3 + 5))) - F(4!)) - (8 \times F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35487 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((-5!)/F(F(4))) - (-F(8) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 35488 &:= ((F(3!) \times (-5^4) + F(8)) + 8!) \\ 35489 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((-5) + F(4!)) + ((8 \times 9)))) \\ 35493 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times 5) + (F(4!) - F(9))) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\ 35494 &:= (-F(F((3 + 5))) + ((F((F(4)!)) \times 9) + F(4!))) \\ 35496 &:= (3! \times (((5 + 4!) \times F(9)) \times 6)) \\ 35497 &:= -(((F(3) + 5) \times ((F(4) - F(9)) - 7!)) \\ 35499 &:= (3 + (((5! - 4) \times 9) \times F(9))) \\ 35511 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((F((5!/5)) + (F(11)))))) \\ 35520 &:= ((F(3!))! + (5! + 5!) \times (-20)) \\ 35523 &:= (((3^5) - ((5 + 2)!)) + (F(3!))!) \\ 35528 &:= ((F(3!)^5) + (5! \times (2 + F(8)))) \\ 35532 &:= (F((3! + (5 + 5))) \times (3!^2)) \\ 35534 &:= -((((F(3!) - 5!) + F(F((5 + 3)))) - F(4!)) \\ 35536 &:= ((F(3!) \times ((5! \times (-5)) + F(3))) + (F(6))!) \\ 35537 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((5! - 5) + F((-((3 - 7)))!))) \\ 35541 &:= -((((F(F((3 + 5))) - 5!) - F(4!)) + 1)) \\ 35542 &:= (((F(F((3 + 5))) - 5!) - F(4!)) \times (-F(2))) \\ 35543 &:= -((((F(F((3 + 5))) - 5!) - F(4!)) - F(F(3)))) \\ 35544 &:= -((((F(F((3 + 5))) - 5!) - F(F(4)) - F(4!))) \\ 35545 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-5) \times ((-5!) \times F((F(4)!)) + (5))) \\ 35546 &:= (-(((F(F(3)) + (-5 - 5!)) - F(4!)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\ 35547 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-5!) + (F((5 + F(4))) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 35548 &:= (((F(F(3)) - (-5 - 5!)) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) \\ 35563 &:= (F((-((F(F(3)) - 5)))!) - ((-5!) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!)))) \\ 35566 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (F((5!/5)) + F((6 + 6)))) \\ 35568 &:= (((F(3) \times 5!)/5) \times (6! + F(8))) \\ 35572 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) + (5! \times 57)) \times 2) \\ 35574 &:= (((F(3) + 5!) + 5!) \times 7) \times F(F((F(4)!))) \\ 35576 &:= ((F(3!) \times ((5! \times (-5)) + 7)) + (F(6))!) \\ 35577 &:= -((F(3!) - ((5^5) \times F(7)) - 7!)) \\ 35584 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((5! \times 5) - 8) \times F((F(4)!))) \\ 35593 &:= (((3! - 5) \times (-5!)) + F((F(9) - F(3!)))) \\ 35594 &:= (((3!/5) - 5) \times (-F(9))) + (F((F(4)!))!) \\ 35596 &:= (((3! \times 5!) + 5) \times F(9)) + F(F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

- 35598** := $((F(3!))! - ((5^5) + F((9 + 8))))$
35614 := $(F(3) \times ((5! + F((F(F(6)) + 1))) - (4!)))$
35616 := $((((F(3!))!/5!) + ((F(6))! - ((1 + 6)!)))$
35617 := $((((F(3!))!/5!) + ((F(6))! - (-1 + 7!)))$
35625 := $((((3 \times 5!) + F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) \times 5)$
35626 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (-((5! - (6^2)))/F(F(6))))$
35627 := $((((3!! \times (-5!) + F(F(6))))/(-2)) - F(7))$
35632 := $-((F(3!) - (((-5!) + F(F(6))) \times 3!)/(-2)))$
35633 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((-((5^6)) - F(3!)) + (F(3!))!))$
35634 := $(-(3!) + (((5! - F(F(6))) \times 3!)/F(F(4))))$
35635 := $((((3!! \times (-5!) + F(F(6))))/(-F(3))) - (5))$
35637 := $((((3 \times 5!) + (F(6))!) + (-3 - 7!))$
35638 := $((F(3!))! - (((5^6) + 3) - F(F(8))))$
35640 := $(3 \times ((5! - F(F(6))) \times ((4 + 0!)!))$
35641 := $((((3!! \times (5! - F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) + 1)$
35642 := $((((3!! \times (5! - F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) + 2)$
35643 := $(3 \times (((5! - F(6)) - F(4))^{F(3)}))$
35644 := $((F(3!)^5) + ((6! \times 4) - (4)))$
35645 := $((((3!! \times (5! - F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) + (5))$
35646 := $((((3!! \times (5! - F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) + 6)$
35647 := $((((3!! \times (5! - F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) + 7)$
35648 := $((((3 \times 5!) + (F(6)^4)) \times 8)$
35649 := $((((3!! \times (5! - F(F(6))))/F(F(4))) + 9)$
35650 := $((((F(3) + (5)) - 6!) \times (-50))$
35654 := $((F(3!)^5) + (6 + (5! \times 4!)))$
35655 := $(3 \times (((-5!) + F(F(6))) \times (-5!)) + (5))$
35660 := $((F(3!))! - (F((5 + F(6))) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
35662 := $(F(3) \times (5! + F((6 + (F(6) \times 2))))$
35664 := $(F(3!) \times (5! - (-6) \times (6! + F(4))))$
35667 := $((((F(3) \times 5!) + (F(6))!) - (F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))))$
35669 := $((((3^5) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((6! \times F(9))))$
35673 := $((F(3!))! - (-5! + (F(F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) - 3!))))$
35675 := $((F(3!))! - (-5! - ((-6!) - F(F(7))) \times 5))$
35676 := $((((F(3!) \times 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - (7!)) \times 6)$
35688 := $((F(3!) \times ((5! - 6!) + F(8))) + 8!)$

- 35694** := $(3! \times (F((5!/6)) - ((F(9) \times 4!)))$
35696 := $((F(3!) + (5! + F(6))) \times (-F(9))) + (F(6))!$
35697 := $((F(3!)! \times (-5))/(-6) + (9 \times F(F(7))))$
35698 := $((3 + 5 + 6!) \times F(9)) + F(F(8))$
35699 := $-((F(F(3!)) + (5! + ((F(6))! - 9!)/9)))$
35718 := $(3 \times ((5! \times (7 + 1)) + F(F(8))))$
35724 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - ((-5) \times F(7)) \times (2 - ((F(4))!)))$
35731 := $((F(3!)! - ((5! + F(F(7))) \times F((3! + 1))))$
35733 := $((3!! \times (-5)) - F((F(7) + 3))) + (F(3!)!)$
35734 := $((((-F(F(3) - (5))))! \times F(7)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(4!)$
35735 := $-((F(F(3)) - ((5! \times F(F(7))) + ((3!^5))))$
35736 := $((3!! + 5!) \times (-F(7))) + (3!^6)$
35742 := $-((3! - (5! \times F(7))) \times (4! - F(2)))$
35743 := $((3 \times (5! - F(7))) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(3!)))$
35744 := $((F(F(3!)) - (5 \times F(F(7)))) \times 4) + (F((F(4))!))!$
35746 := $-((((F(3) + 5))! - ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) + (F(6))!)))$
35748 := $((-(3! \times (5! + 7))) \times (F(4))! + 8!)$
35757 := $(-3) + (5! \times (F(F(7)) - (-5) \times F(7)))$
35759 := $((-3) - 5!) + (F(F(7)) \times (5! + F(9)))$
35760 := $((F(3!)! - ((-5) + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
35763 := $((F(F(3!)) \times ((-5) - F(F(7))) + F(F(6)))) + (F(3!)!)$
35764 := $((3! \times 57) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(4!)$
35766 := $((3 \times (-5!) + (F(F(7)) \times (-6)))) + (F(6))!$
35767 := $((((3 + 5))! - F(F(7))) + (6! - 7!))$
35768 := $(((((F(3!)!)/5!) + F(F(7))) \times (-F(6))) + 8!)$
35770 := $((F(3) + 5) \times (7! + 70))$
35773 := $((F(3!)! - (5! - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7) + 3!))))$
35776 := $(((((F(3)^5) - 7!) \times (-7)) + 6!))$
35777 := $((3! + ((5 \times F(7)) + 7!)) \times 7)$
35778 := $(3! \times ((57 - 7!) + F(F(8))))$
35780 := $((F(3!)! - (-5!) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(8) - 0!)))$
35784 := $((3! - (-5) \times F(7)) \times (F(8) \times 4!))$
35786 := $(((-3) \times (5! + 7!)) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!$
35787 := $((3 \times 5!) + ((7! + F(8)) \times 7))$
35789 := $((F(F(3!)) \times 5!) + F(F(7))) \times (-F(8) - F(9))$

$$\begin{aligned} 35794 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((5! + F(7)) \times F(9)) + (4))) \\ 35796 &:= (((F(3!) \times 5!) + (7! - F(9))) \times 6) \\ 35797 &:= (3!! + (((5 + 7!) - F(9)) \times 7)) \\ 35798 &:= -((((3! + 5!) + (7)) \times F(9)) - 8!) \\ 35814 &:= ((F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times (F(8) + F(F((1 + (F(4)!)))))) \\ 35824 &:= (((F(3!)^5) + 8!)/2) - ((F(4)!))! \\ 35826 &:= (((3!! + F((-5) + F(8)))) - F(2)) \times F(F(6)) \\ 35829 &:= -((3!! - ((5! - F((F(8) - 2))) \times (-9)))) \\ 35833 &:= (((3 + 5!) - F(F(8))) + (3!^{3!})) \\ 35834 &:= ((F((F(F(3!)) - 5)) + (F(F(8))/(-F(3)))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\ 35836 &:= (((3! + 5!) - F(F(8))) + (3!^6)) \\ 35839 &:= -((3! - (5)) + ((-8!) \times F(3!))/(-9)) \\ 35840 &:= (F(3!) \times ((5! - 8) \times 40)) \\ 35843 &:= (((F(F(F(3!)))/5 + F(8)) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\ 35844 &:= -((3!! - ((5! - (F(8)^{F(4)})) \times (-4)))) \\ 35845 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-5 + (8!/(4 + 5)))) \\ 35846 &:= (-F(F(3)) + ((F((-5) + F(8)) + ((F(4)!))! \times F(F(6)))) \\ 35847 &:= ((3!! + F((-5) + F(8))) \times (F(4) \times 7)) \\ 35848 &:= (F(F(3)) + ((F((-5) + F(8)) + ((F(4)!))! \times F(8))) \\ 35849 &:= (((F(3!))! - (5 + F(F(8)))) + (((F(4)!))! \times 9)) \\ 35854 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((5 + 8) \times 5) \times ((F(4)!))!)) \\ 35856 &:= (((3!! \times 5) - (8!/5)) + (F(6))!) \\ 35863 &:= (F((-((F(F(3)) - 5)))!) - (F(F(8)) - (F(F(6))^{F(3)}))) \\ 35864 &:= (((-3) \times 5!) + 8!) - (F(6)^4) \\ 35866 &:= ((35 \times (-8) + 6!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 35868 &:= (((F(3) + 5!) \times F(8)) \times (6 + 8)) \\ 35873 &:= (((F(3!))! + 5) - ((-F(8) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(3!)))) \\ 35874 &:= (((F(3!) \times 5!) - (F(8) - 7!)) \times (F(4))!) \\ 35877 &:= (((F((3 \times 5)) + 8!) - 7!) - F(7)) \\ 35878 &:= ((3!! \times (-5)) - ((F(F(8))/F(7)) - 8!)) \\ 35880 &:= (F(3!) \times (5 - (8!/(-8 - 0!)))) \\ 35887 &:= ((-3) + F((5!/8))) + (8! - 7!) \\ 35889 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times ((5! - 8) + F((8 + 9)))) \\ 35896 &:= (((F(3) + 5) + (8!/9)) \times F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35903 &:= (F(F(3!)) + ((5! + F(9)) \times F(F((0! + 3!)))))) \\ 35913 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - (5)))! - ((F(9) - 1)^3))) \\ 35917 &:= ((F(3) + (5)) \times (91 + 7!)) \\ 35924 &:= -((F(3!) - (-5) + ((F(9) - F(2))^{F(4)}))) \\ 35934 &:= (-3) + (((5 + F(9)) - 3!)^{F(4)}) \\ 35936 &:= (((35 \times F(9)) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 35937 &:= (-(((3! - (5)) - F(9)))^{F(-3+7)}) \\ 35939 &:= -(((F(F(3!)) - 5!) + ((-9!) + (F(3!))!)/9)) \\ 35943 &:= (3! + (((-5) + F(9)) + (4))^3) \\ 35944 &:= ((F(3) + (5)) + ((9 + 4!)^{F(4)})) \\ 35946 &:= (((3 + 5)! - (9^{F(4)}) \times 6) \\ 35950 &:= (((3!)! - F(F(F(-((5 - 9)))))) \times 50) \\ 35952 &:= (((F(3!)!)/(-5!)) - (9!/(-5 \times 2))) \\ 35962 &:= ((F(3!)^5) - (F((9 + F(6))) \times (-2))) \\ 35964 &:= (((F(3!) + 5!) \times (-F(9))) + (F(6))! - 4) \\ 35966 &:= (((3 + 5)! - F(9)) + (6! \times (-6))) \\ 35967 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((5! \times F(9)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7)))) \\ 35968 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - (5)) \times (-F(9) \times F(6))) + 8!) \\ 35969 &:= ((F(3!)! + ((5! + 9) + ((F(6))!/(-9)))) \\ 35971 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) - (5 \times ((F(9) - 7!) + 1))) \\ 35973 &:= (((F(F(3)) + 5!) \times (-F(9))) - F(F(7))) + (F(3!)!) \\ 35974 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + ((-5) \times (F(9) - 7!) - F(F(4)))) \\ 35976 &:= (((3!)! - ((5 - 9))!) - (7!)) + (F(6))! \\ 35978 &:= ((F(3) + (-5) \times (F(9) - 7!)) + F(F(8))) \\ 35984 &:= (-3!) + (59 \times F((F(8) - (F(4))!))) \\ 35985 &:= (((3!)! - ((F((5 + 9)) \times F(8)))) \times (-5)) \\ 35990 &:= ((F(3) - 5!) \times ((F(9) \times (-9)) + 0!)) \\ 35993 &:= (3 - (-59) \times F((9 + 3!))) \\ 35994 &:= (((3!)! \times (59 - 9)) - (F(4))!) \\ 35996 &:= (3! + (59 \times F((9 + 6)))) \\ 35998 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - (5! \times 9)) \times (-F(9))) - 8) \\ 36006 &:= (-((3! \times (6! - 0!))) + (F(06))!) \\ 36007 &:= ((3!)! + ((F(6) - 0!) \times (0! + 7!))) \\ 36019 &:= ((F(3!)! - (((6 - 0!)! + (F(19))))) \end{aligned}$$

- 36024** := $((F(3!))! - ((6! \times ((0! + 2))!) - (4!)))$
- 36025** := $((F(3) \times 6!) + 0!) \times 25$
- 36026** := $(F(F(F(3!))) - (6 \times (0! - F((-2) + F(F(6))))))$
- 36032** := $(F(F(F(3!))) - (-6 \times F(((0! + F(F(3!))) - F(2))))$
- 36034** := $((F(3!))! + ((F((F(6) + 0!)) - ((3!)! \times (F(4)!))))$
- 36036** := $((3! - 6!) \times (03!) + (F(6))!)$
- 36037** := $((((3!)! - F((F(F(6)) - 0!))) \times (-3!)) - F(F(7)))$
- 36038** := $((F((-F(3) + F(F(6)))) + 0!) \times 3!) + F(F(8))$
- 36042** := $((F(F(3!)) + ((6! \times (0! + 4!)))) \times 2$
- 36048** := $((F(3!) - 6!) \times (F(04))!) + 8!$
- 36050** := $((F(3) + 6!) - 0!) \times 50$
- 36053** := $((F(3) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (((0! - 5!)^{F(3)}))$
- 36073** := $((((F(3!))! / (-F(6) + 0!)) + F(F(7))) + (F(3!))!)$
- 36078** := $-(((3! \times (6! - F(07))) - 8!))$
- 36084** := $(-3!) \times (((F(6))! + F((0! + 8))) - F(4!))$
- 36094** := $((F(3!))! - F(F(F(6)))) - (((0! - 9))! / (-F(4)!))$
- 36096** := $((F((3! + F(6))) - 0!) \times 96$
- 36099** := $((F(F(3!)) + ((F(6))! / (-0! + 9))) \times (-9)$
- 36105** := $((F(F(3!)) + (6! \times 10)) \times 5$
- 36118** := $((F(3!))! - (F(F(6)) + F((1 + 18))))$
- 36119** := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(6)) + (-1 + F(19))))$
- 36125** := $((F(F(F(3!))) - (61^2)) \times 5$
- 36126** := $((((3!)! - F(F(6))) \times (-((1 + 2)!)) + (F(6))!)$
- 36131** := $(-((F(3!) - (F(6))!)) - F(((1 + F(F(3!))) - 1)))$
- 36132** := $(((-3!) + (F(6))! - 1) - F((F(F(3!)) - 2)))$
- 36133** := $((-3!) + (F(6))! - F((13 + 3!)))$
- 36134** := $((3!)! - F(F(F(6)))) - (F(((1 \times 3)!)) - F(4!))$
- 36135** := $-(((F((-F(3) + F(F(6)))) - 1) - (F(3!))! + (5)))$
- 36136** := $((-3) + (F(6))! - F((13 + 6)))$
- 36137** := $((-F(3) + (F(6))! - F(((1 \times 3)! + F(7))))$
- 36138** := $((-F((3 \times 6) + 1)) - F(F(3))) + 8!$
- 36139** := $((F(3) + (6))! - F((1 + (F(3) \times 9))))$
- 36140** := $((F(3!))! - ((F((-((6 - 1)) + 4!)) - 0!))$
- 36141** := $((3!)! - F(F(F(6)))) + (-1 + F(((4 \times 1)!))$
- 36142** := $((3!)! + (F((F(6) + 14)) \times 2))$

- 36143** := $((((3!)! - F(F(F(6)))) - (-1 - F((4 \times 3!))))$
36144 := $(3! \times (((F(6))! \times (-1)) - (4!)) + F(4!))$
36145 := $((3! + (F(6))!) - F((14 + 5)))$
36146 := $((3 - F(F(F(6)))) - ((-1 - F(4!)) - (6!)))$
36147 := $((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((1 + 4) \times 7!))$
36148 := $((3! + 6!) + F(((1 \times 4)!)) - F(F(8)))$
36149 := $((-(F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - 1) + (F((F(4))!))! + 9)$
36152 := $((3!)! + ((F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (5)) \times 2))$
36154 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (((6 + 1)! \times 5) + F((F(4))!)))$
36156 := $((F(3) + ((6 + 1)! \times 5) + F(F(F(6))))$
36160 := $((F(3!))! + (F(F(6)))) - F((-1 + F(F(6)) - 0!))$
36162 := $(3! \times (((6 + 1)! + F((F(6) \times 2))))$
36163 := $((F(3) \times F((F(F(6)) + 1))) + ((F(F(6)) + 3!)))$
36163 := $((F(3) \times F((F(F(6)) + 1))) + ((F(F(6)) + 3!)))$
36164 := $((3!)! - F(F(F(6)))) - ((-1 - F(F(6))) - F(4!))$
36167 := $((F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (-((1 - 6) \times 7!))$
36175 := $-(((F(3!))! - (((F(F(F(6))) - 1) \times 7) - 5!)))$
36184 := $((3!)! + ((F(F(6)) + F((1 + F(8)))) \times F(F(4)))$
36194 := $((F((F(3) + F(6))) - (F(19))) + (F((F(4))!))!)$
36198 := $-(((3! \times ((6! + 1) - F(9))) - 8!))$
36222 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(6))^{2+2} + 2))$
36223 := $-(((F(F(3)) - (F(6))!) + ((2 + 2)^{3!}))$
36224 := $-(((F(3))^{6 \times 2} - ((2 \times 4)!))$
36225 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) - ((2 + 5)!))$
36226 := $((F(3) + (F(6))!) - ((2 + 2)^6))$
36227 := $((3 + (F(6))!) - (2^{-F(2)+F(7)}))$
36232 := $((F(3!) + (F(6))!) - ((2^{3!})^2)$
36233 := $((F(3!))! + F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) - (3! \times (3!))$
36234 := $(-3!) \times (((F(6))! + F(2)) + F(3!)) - F(4!))$
36237 := $((F(3!))! - (((6 - 2)^{3!}) - F(7)))$
36239 := $-(((F(F(3)) - (F(6))!) + (((2 + 3)! \times F(9))))$
36240 := $((F(3!))! - (F((F(6) + F(2))) \times ((4 + 0!)!))$
36243 := $((F(3!))! + ((F(F(6)) - (2 + (4^{3!}))))$
36244 := $((F(3!))! + (((F(F(6)) - F(2)) - (4^{F(4)!})))$

$$\begin{aligned} 36247 &:= (((F(3!)!) \times (F(F(6)) - 2)) / F(F((F(4)!))) - F(F(7))) \\ 36248 &:= -((((F(3)^{6 \times 2}) - 4!) - 8!)) \\ 36253 &:= (((F(3!)!) - F((F(F(6)) - 2))) + (5! - 3!)) \\ 36256 &:= ((-3) - F((F(F(6)) - 2))) - (-5!) - (F(6)!)) \\ 36258 &:= (3! \times (F(((6 - 2)!)) - (5 + 8!))) \\ 36259 &:= ((F(3!)!) + ((F(F(6)) + (-2) - (5! \times F(9)))))) \\ 36264 &:= (((3 + 6)! / (2 + F(6))) - 4!) \\ 36265 &:= (((F(3!)!) - F((F(F(6)) - 2))) + (6 + 5!)) \\ 36267 &:= (F((F(3) \times F(6))) + (((2 + 6)! - 7!)) \\ 36270 &:= (((3!)! - F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) \times (-7 + 0!)) \\ 36273 &:= ((F(3!)!) + ((F((F(6) \times 2)) - ((7! - 3!)))))) \\ 36274 &:= (((F(3) \times 6!) + 2) \times (-7)) + F(4!) \\ 36275 &:= ((F(3!)!) - ((6! + F((-2) + F(7)))) \times 5) \\ 36276 &:= (F((3 \times F(6))) + (-2) \times (7! + (6))) \\ 36278 &:= -((((F(3!)!) + (((6 - 2)! + (-7) \times F(F(8)))))) \\ 36279 &:= (F((3 \times F(6))) + ((-2) \times 7! - 9)) \\ 36282 &:= (3! \times (-((6! - 2) + F((F(8) - F(2)))))) \\ 36283 &:= ((F(3!)!) - (-F((6 \times 2))) + F((F(8) - F(3)))) \\ 36286 &:= (-F(3) + (((F(6)! / (-2 + 8)) + (F(6)!)) \\ 36287 &:= -((((F(F(3)) + (F(6)!)) - ((-2) + F(F(8))) \times 7)) \\ 36288 &:= ((3! \times ((6^2) \times 8)) \times F(8)) \\ 36289 &:= (F(F(3)) + (((F(6)! / (-2 + 8)) \times (-9))) \\ 36290 &:= (F(3) + (((F(6) + F(2))! / (9 + 0!))) \\ 36291 &:= (3 + (((F(6) + F(2))! / (9 + 1))) \\ 36292 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) + ((6! \times (F(2) + 9)))) \times 2) \\ 36293 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) \times (F(6) - F(2))) + (-9 - (F(3!)!)) \\ 36294 &:= (((3^{F(6)}) - 2^9) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 36295 &:= ((F(3!)!) + ((F((F(6) + 2)) - ((F(9) \times 5!)))) \\ 36296 &:= (((3 + 6)! / (F(2) + 9)) + F(6)) \\ 36301 &:= -((((F(3!)!) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times (3! + 0!)) - 1))) \\ 36302 &:= (((F(3!)!) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (3! + 0!))) \times (-F(2))) \\ 36303 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(F(6)))) / 3) + 0!) - (F(3!)!) \\ 36304 &:= ((F(3) \times (F(6) - ((3! + 0!)!)) + F(4!)) \\ 36306 &:= (((3 - (F(6)!)) + F(((3 + 0!)!)) \times 6) \\ 36307 &:= ((-F(3) - (F(6)!)) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + 0!) \times 7)) \end{aligned}$$

- 36308** := $((3! - (F(6))!) + ((3! + 0!) \times F(F(8))))$
36309 := $((3!)! + F(F(6))) \times (-3!) + F((0! + 9)))$
36316 := $((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (3! + 1)) - (F(6))!$
36317 := $((F(3!) - (F(6))!) + ((F(F(F(3!)))) + 1) \times 7)$
36318 := $(3! \times ((-6!) + F(3!)) + F((-1 + F(8))))$
36323 := $((3 + F(F(F(6)))) \times (3! + F(2))) - (F(3!))!$
36324 := $(3! \times ((6 - (F(3 \times 2)))!) + F(4!))$
36328 := $(F(3!) \times ((6!/F(3)) + F((-2) + F(8))))$
36334 := $(-F(3)) + (6 \times ((F(3!) - (F(3!))!) + F(4!)))$
36336 := $(3! \times ((F((F(6) \times 3)) + F(3!)) - (F(6))!))$
36337 := $-(((F(3!))! + ((F((F(6) \times F(3)))/(-3)) \times F(F(7))))$
36338 := $((((-3!) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-3!)) - (F(3!))! + F(F(8)))$
36342 := $(-3!) \times (((F(6))! - F(3!)) - F(4!)) - F(2))$
36343 := $((F(3!))! - ((63^{F(4)}) + F(3!)))$
36344 := $(F(3!) - (((F(6))! - F(3!)) - F(4!)) \times (F(4!)))$
36345 := $((F(F(3)) + (F(6))!) - ((F(3!)^4) - 5!))$
36347 := $-((F(F(3)) - ((F(F(6)) - 3!) \times (-4) \times F(7))))$
36348 := $((3! + F((F(6) \times F(3)))) \times (-4) + 8!)$
36349 := $((-F(3)) + (F(6))!) + ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)}) \times (-9))$
36351 := $-(((3 \times F(F(6)))^{F(3)} - (F((5 + 1)))!))$
36352 := $((F(3)^{F(6)}) \times (((3!)!/5) - 2))$
36354 := $(-3!) \times (((F(6))! - ((3! + 5))) - F(4!))$
36356 := $-((((3 \times F(F(6)))^{F(3)} - 5) - (F(6))!))$
36357 := $(3 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(3!) + (5 \times F(F(7))))))$
36358 := $(((-F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(3) + 5)) - 8!$
36360 := $((F(3!))! - (6 \times ((3!)! - 60))$
36364 := $-(((F(3!) - (F(6))!) + (F((F(3) \times F(6))) \times 4))$
36365 := $((3!)! - ((F(6) - (3^{F(6)}))) \times 5)$
36366 := $((-F(3)) + F(F(6))) \times (-3!) + ((F(6))!/F(F(6))))$
36367 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) - ((F((F(6) - F(F(3)))) - 6) \times 7))$
36371 := $((F(3!))! - F((F(F(6)) - F(3))) + ((F(F(7)) - 1))$
36372 := $((F(3!))! - ((-F(6)) \times F((3 + F(7))))/(-2))$
36373 := $((F(3!))! - F((F(F(6)) - F(3))) + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(3))))$
36374 := $((F(3) + (F(6))!) - (F((3 + F(7))) \times 4))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36376 &:= (((3! \times 6!) - 3!) + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\
 36377 &:= (((3!)! + F((F(6) + 3!))) - (7! \times (-7))) \\
 36378 &:= ((3! - F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) + (F(F(7)) + 8!)) \\
 36379 &:= (((F(3!)! - (F(F(6)))) - (((F(3!)! - (7!))/9)) \\
 36384 &:= (F(3) \times ((6! + 38) \times 4!)) \\
 36385 &:= ((-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times (((F(3!)!)/F(8)) - (5))) \\
 36393 &:= ((F(3!)! - (-F(F(6))) \times ((F(F(3!)) \times (-9)) + F(3))) \\
 36396 &:= (((3!)! + (((6^{3!}) - F(9)))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 36397 &:= (-3) + ((-6!) + ((F(3!)!)/(-9))) \times (-7) \\
 36405 &:= (((3^{F(6)}) + ((F(4)!)!) \times 05) \\
 36407 &:= ((-F(3) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F((F(F((F(4)!)!)) - 0!)) \times (-7))) \\
 36408 &:= (((F((F(3) \times F(6))) + F(4!)) - 0!) - F(F(8))) \\
 36409 &:= ((F((F(3) \times F(6))) + F(4!)) - F(F(-(0! - 9)))) \\
 36414 &:= (3! - 6!)^{F(F(4))} / 14 \\
 36417 &:= ((F(3!) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F((F(F((F(4)!)!)) - 1)) \times (-7))) \\
 36423 &:= (((F(3!)!)/F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times (-2 + F(F(3!))) \\
 36424 &:= (((3! \times 6!) + F(F(((F(4)!)! + F(2)))) \times F((F(4)!)!)) \\
 36426 &:= (-((3 \times ((6^4) + 2))) + (F(6))!) \\
 36428 &:= ((3!)! + (((6^{F(4)!}) - 2) - F(F(8)))) \\
 36429 &:= ((-3) \times ((F(F(6)))! - ((4!)!)))/(F(-(F(2) - 9)))! \\
 \\
 36430 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 0 \\
 36431 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 1 \\
 36432 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 2 \\
 36433 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 3 \\
 36434 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 4 \\
 36435 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 5 \\
 36436 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 6 \\
 36437 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 7 \\
 36438 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 8 \\
 36439 &:= 3!! - F(F(F(6))) + F(4)!^{3!} + 9 \\
 \\
 36442 &:= ((-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times (((F((F(4)!)!))!)/F(F((F(4)!)!))) - 2) \\
 36443 &:= (F(3!) + (((F(F(6)))! + ((4!)!) \times F(4))/(F(F(3!))!)) \\
 36444 &:= (((F(3) - (F(6))!) + (4!)) + F(4!)) \times (F(4)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 36445 := $((-(F(F(3))) - F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4!) + (4^5))))$
- 36446 := $((F(3)^{6+4}) + F(4!) - F(F(F(6))))$
- 36447 := $((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(F(6)))) / (F(4)!) + (F((F(4)!) \times (-F(F(7)))))$
- 36448 := $((F(3) \times F(6)) + ((F(4) \times (4!)!) / (F(8)!))$
- 36449 := $((-(F(3)!)!) - ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F((F(4)!)!))) \times (F(F(4)) - 9)))$
- 36452 := $((((3!)! - F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) \times 52)$
- 36453 := $((F(3)!)! + ((F(F(6)) - ((F(4)!)^5) / F(3))))$
- 36454 := $((F(3!) - F(F(F(6)))) - (-((4^5) - F(4!)))$
- 36456 := $((3! + F(6)) \times (4 + 5!)) \times F(F(6))$
- 36457 := $((F(F(3)) + (F(6))!) - (F(4!) / (5 + 7)))$
- 36460 := $(((-F(3)!) + F(F(F(6)))) / (F(4)!) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!))$
- 36461 := $((-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times (((F((F(4)!)!)! / F(F(6))) - 1))$
- 36462 := $((3! + (F(6))!) - (F(4!) / (6 \times 2)))$
- 36464 := $((F(3!) + (F(6))!) - (F(4!) / (F(6) + (4))))$
- 36465 := $((3! \times F(6)) + F(4)) \times (6! - (5))$
- 36467 := $((F(3)!)! - (((F(6))! \times F(F(4))) / F(F(6))) + F(7))$
- 36468 := $(3! \times (6 + ((4!)! / ((F(F(6))!) + ((F(8)!)!))))$
- 36469 := $((3 \times (((F(F(6))!) + ((4!)!) / (F(F(6))!)) + F(9)))$
- 36470 := $((F(3)!)! - (F((6 + 4)) \times 70))$
- 36471 := $((-(F(3)!)! + (((F(F(F(6))) + (4!)) \times (-7)) - 1)))$
- 36472 := $((-(F(3)!)! - (((F(F(F(6))) + (4!)) \times 7) + 2)))$
- 36473 := $(((((F(3)!)! / F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(4)))) - 7) + (F(3)!)!)$
- 36474 := $((-3!) \times (((F(6))! - F(4!)) - (7 + 4!)))$
- 36475 := $(((((F(3)!)! / F(F(6))) \times ((F(4)!) + F(7))) - (5)))$
- 36476 := $(3! + (((F(F(F(6))) + (4!)) \times 7) - (F(6))!))$
- 36478 := $((-F(3) + (((F(6))! \times ((F(4)!) + F(7))) / F(8)))$
- 36479 := $(F(3) - ((F(-((F(6) - 4!))) - (7!)) \times 9))$
- 36480 := $((-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times (4! \times 80))$
- 36481 := $((F(3)!)! + (((F(6))! \times F(F(4))) / (-F(8))) + 1)$
- 36482 := $((F(3)!)! - (((F(6))! \times F(F(4))) / F(8)) - 2)$
- 36484 := $((F(3!) - ((6 + 4) \times F(F(8)))) / (-F(4)))$
- 36485 := $((F(3)!)! - (((F(6))! \times F(F(4))) / F(8)) - (5))$
- 36486 := $(3! - (((F(6))! \times F(F(4))) / F(8)) - (F(6))!)$
- 36487 := $(((-3) \times 6!) \times (4 - F(8))) - F(F(7))$
- 36488 := $(F(3!) + ((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) \times (8! / F(8))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36489 &:= (-3) + (6 \times (F(4!) - ((8! - F(9)))))) \\
 36490 &:= (((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4)) \times (9 + 0!)) \\
 36491 &:= ((F((3! + F(6))) + (4!)) \times 91) \\
 36492 &:= (3 \times (((F(6))! - F(4!)) - F(9)) \times (-2)) \\
 36493 &:= (F(F(3)) + (((F(6))! - F(4!)) - F(9)) \times (-3!)) \\
 36494 &:= (F(3) - (((F(6))! - F(4!)) - F(9)) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 36495 &:= (3 \times (F(F(6)) + ((4!)/(F(F((F((9 - 5))))!)))))) \\
 36496 &:= ((F(3!) \times (-((F(6)^{F(4)}) - F(9)))) + (F(6)!)) \\
 36523 &:= (((F(3!))! + (F(6)^5)/2) - F(F(3!))) \\
 36533 &:= ((F(3) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (((5! + F(F(3)))^{F(3)})) \\
 36534 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((6! - F((5 + 3!))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 36536 &:= (((F(3!))! + (F(6)^5)/F(3)) - F(6)) \\
 36537 &:= (((F(3!))! + (F(6)^5)/F(3)) - 7) \\
 36542 &:= (((F(3!))! + ((F(6)^5) - (4)))/2) \\
 36543 &:= (((F(3!))! - (-((F(6)^5) + F(F(4)))))/F(3)) \\
 36544 &:= ((F(3)^6) \times (-5) + (4! \times 4!)) \\
 36549 &:= (((3!)/(-6) + F((-5) + 4!)) \times 9) \\
 36564 &:= (-((F(3) - (6)) \times (-5!) + (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 36566 &:= (((F(3) \times F(F(6))) \times F((5!/F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 36567 &:= ((3 - 6!) \times (5 - (F(6) \times 7))) \\
 36573 &:= (((F(3!))! - (6! \times 5)) + (-7) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 36574 &:= (((3!)/(-6) + F((-5) + 4!)) \times 9) \\
 36575 &:= (F((F(3) + F(6))) \times ((5! + F(7)) \times 5)) \\
 36576 &:= (36 \times ((5! + (7)) \times F(6))) \\
 36578 &:= ((F(3) \times ((6^5) + 7!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 36582 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F((6 + 5)) \times F(8)) \times 2)) \\
 36584 &:= (((-3) \times (6! - 5!)) + F(F(8))) \times 4) \\
 36587 &:= (F((F(3) + F(F(6)))) - (F((5!/8)) \times (-F(7)))) \\
 36592 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(F(6)) - (5)) \times F(F((9 - 2)))))) \\
 36594 &:= ((3 + (F(6) \times 5!)) \times (F(9) + (4))) \\
 \\
 36600 &:= F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 0 \\
 36601 &:= F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 1 \\
 36602 &:= F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 2 \\
 36603 &:= F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$36604 := F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 4$$

$$36605 := F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 5$$

$$36606 := F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 6$$

$$36607 := F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 7$$

$$36608 := F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 8$$

$$36609 := F(-3! + F(F(6))) \times 60 + 9$$

$$36615 := ((F(3!))! - ((6! + F(F(6))) \times (1 \times 5)))$$

$$36624 := ((F(3!))! - (F(F(6)) \times (F(6) \times (-2) + 4!)))$$

$$36625 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(F(6)) + ((6! - 2))) \times 5))$$

$$36632 := ((F(3!) + ((F(6))!/F(F(6)))) \times (F(F(3!)) - 2))$$

$$36639 := ((F(3!))! - (F(F(6)) + (6 \times F((3! + 9))))$$

$$36640 := -((F(F(F(3!))) - (66 \times (((F(4))!)! + 0!))))$$

$$36642 := ((F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + F((F(F(6)) - (F(4))!))) \times 2)$$

$$36643 := -(((F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6)) \times (-4!))) - (F(3!))!))$$

$$36645 := ((F(3!))! - (F(F(6)) \times ((6!/4) - (5))))$$

$$36647 := ((3! \times ((F(F(6)) - (F(6))!) + F(4!))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$36648 := ((3 \times (-6!) + (F(F(6)) \times (-4!))) + 8!)$$

$$36650 := (((3!)! - F(6)) + F(F(6))) \times 50$$

$$36654 := ((-3!) + (F(6))!) - (6 \times F((5 \times F(4))))$$

$$36655 := ((F(3!))! - (((F(6) + 6!) + (5)) \times 5))$$

$$36656 := ((-((F(3)^6)) + (F(6))!) - (5 \times 6!))$$

$$36658 := ((-F(3)) + (F(6))!) - (6 \times F((5!/8)))$$

$$36660 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 0$$

$$36661 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 1$$

$$36662 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 2$$

$$36663 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 3$$

$$36664 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 4$$

$$36665 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 5$$

$$36666 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 6$$

$$36667 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 7$$

$$36668 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 8$$

$$36669 := F(3!)! - 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 6) + 9$$

$$36672 := ((F(3!))! - (6 \times (F((F(6) + (7)))) - 2)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36673 &:= (((-3!) \times F((F(F(6)) - 6))) + F(7)) + (F(3)!))! \\
 36674 &:= ((F(3)! - ((-F(6) + F((F(6) + F(7)))))/F(4))) \\
 36677 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - (F(6)!)) + ((-6) \times F(F(7))) + (7!))) \\
 36684 &:= (3! \times ((66 - 8!) + F(4!))) \\
 36686 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (((F(F(6)) - F(6))!)/(8! \times 6))) \\
 36690 &:= ((F(3)! - (66 \times F((9 + 0!)))) \\
 36694 &:= (((-3!) \times F((F(F(6)) - 6))) + F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!) \\
 36696 &:= (3 \times ((6! \times (F(6) + 9)) - F(6))) \\
 36697 &:= (((3!^6) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F((9 + 7)))) \\
 36699 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - (((6!/(-6)) \times F(9)) \times (-9))) \\
 36714 &:= (-3!) \times (((F(6)! - (71)) - F(4!))) \\
 36715 &:= ((F(3)! - (((((F(F(6))/7)! + 1) \times 5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36720 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 0 \\
 36721 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 1 \\
 36722 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 2 \\
 36723 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 3 \\
 36724 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 4 \\
 36725 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 5 \\
 36726 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 6 \\
 36727 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 7 \\
 36728 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 8 \\
 36729 &:= F(3)! + 6! \times (-7 + 2) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36731 &:= ((F(3) + F(F(6))) \times F((-7) + ((3 + 1)!)) \\
 36733 &:= (((3!)! + (F(6)!)) + F(7)) - (3! \times (3)!)) \\
 36734 &:= (((((3!)! + F(F(6))) \times (-F(7))) - F(F(3))) + F(4!)) \\
 36735 &:= ((3!)! + (F(F(6)) \times ((7^3) \times 5))) \\
 36736 &:= (((F(3)^{F(6)}) \times (-7)) \times F(3)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 36737 &:= ((3! \times ((6 \times F(7))^{F(3)})) + F(F(7))) \\
 36738 &:= (((F((-3!) + F(F(6)))) - F(7)) \times (-3!)) + 8! \\
 36739 &:= ((3 + (F(6)!)) + (-7) \times (F(3)^9)) \\
 36741 &:= (F(F(3!)) + (6! \times ((F(7) \times 4) - 1))) \\
 36743 &:= (((((3!)! + F(F(6))) \times (-F(7))) + F(4!)) + F(3!)) \\
 36745 &:= ((F(3)! - (((6! - (7)) + F(F(4))) \times 5))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 36746** := $(-(3) + (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7)))) / (-F(4))) + (F(6))!))$
- 36747** := $((3! \times (6! + 7!)) + (F(4)^7))$
- 36749** := $((F(3))! - (F((6 + F(7))) - F((4! - 9))))$
- 36750** := $((F(3) + 6!) + F(7)) \times 50$
- 36753** := $((F(3))! - (((6! - (7)) \times 5) + F(3)))$
- 36754** := $((F(3))! - ((6! - (7)) \times 5) - F(F(F(4))))$
- 36756** := $((F(F(3)) + ((6! - (7)) \times (-5))) + (F(6))!)$
- 36757** := $-(((F(3))! + ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) \times 5)) \times (-7))))$
- 36762** := $((F(3))! - (6 \times (F(F(7)) - (6! / (-2))))$
- 36764** := $((F(3!) - F(F(6))) \times ((F(7) - 6!) \times 4))$
- 36770** := $((F(3))! - ((F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(7))) + 0!))$
- 36771** := $((F(3))! - (F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F((7 \times 1))))$
- 36772** := $((F(3))! - ((F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(7))) - F(2)))$
- 36773** := $((F(3))! - ((F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(7))) - F(3)))$
- 36774** := $-(((F(F(3)) + (6! \times F(7))) + F(F(7))) - F(4!))$
- 36776** := $((F(3) \times 6!) + (7 \times (7! + F(6))))$
- 36777** := $((3!)! - (F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(7)))) \times (-F(7))$
- 36783** := $(((-F((3 \times 6))) - F(F(7))) + 8! - 3!)$
- 36784** := $((3! \times (-6) + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) - F(4!)))$
- 36786** := $((3! \times (F(F(6)) - (F((7 + 8)))) + (F(6))!)$
- 36792** := $((((3 + 6))! + 7!) / (9 + F(2)))$
- 36793** := $((F(F(3)) + (F(6))! - ((7 \times 9!) / (3!)!))$
- 36794** := $((F(3) + (F(6))! - ((7 \times 9!) / ((F(4))!))$
- 36797** := $((F(3))! - (((F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(9)) - F(7)))$
- 36813** := $((F(F(3)) \times (-((F(6) \times F(8)) - 1))) + (F(3))!)$
- 36814** := $(F(3) \times ((6! + F((F(8) + 1))) - (4!)))$
- 36824** := $((F(3))! - (F(6) \times ((F(8)^2) - (4))))$
- 36825** := $((F(3))! - (((6! - F(8)) \times F(2)) \times 5))$
- 36832** := $(F(3) \times ((F(6))! + ((F(F(8)) + 3!) \times (-2))))$
- 36834** := $-((3! \times (6! - ((F(8) - F(3))^{F(4)})))$
- 36835** := $((F(3))! - (((6! - F(8)) - F(3)) \times 5))$
- 36838** := $((((3!)! + (F(6))!) - F((F(8) - F(3)))) - (F(8)))$
- 36840** := $((F(3))! - ((F(6) + F(8)) \times ((4 + 0!)!))$
- 36842** := $-(((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))) - ((8 \times 4!)^2)))$

- 36843** := $-((F((F(3) + (6))) - ((8 \times 4!)^{F(3)})))$
36844 := $((F(3) \times (F(6)!) - ((F(F(8)) + F(4)) \times 4))$
36845 := $((F(3)!)! - (((6! - F(8)) - (4)) \times 5))$
36846 := $((3!)! + ((-((6! - F(8))) \times (F(4)!) + (F(6)!)!))$
36848 := $(F(3) \times (((F(6)!) - F(F(8))) - 4) - F(F(8)))$
36849 := $((3! - F(F(6))) + ((8^4) \times 9))$
36854 := $-(((F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - ((8! - (5)))) - ((F(4)!)!))$
36856 := $(F(3) \times ((F(6)!) - (F(F(8)) \times F((-5) + F(6))))))$
36859 := $((F(3)!)! - (((6! - F(8)) \times 5) - F(9)))$
36860 := $-((F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - ((8! + 6!) + 0!))$
36862 := $((F((3 \times F(6))) - F(F(8))) + (6! \times 2))$
36865 := $((F(3)!)! - (((6! - F(8)) - F(6)) \times 5))$
36866 := $((((3!)! + (F(6)!) + F(F(8))) + (-6!) \times F(F(6))))$
36867 := $((F(3!) + ((6! + 8!)) - F((6 + F(7))))$
36868 := $(F(3) \times (((F(6)!) - F(F(8))) + 6) - F(F(8)))$
36874 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(6)) \times (-F(8)))) - ((F(F(7)) - F(4)!)))$
36875 := $((3^6) + F(F(8))) - (7! \times (-5))$
36876 := $((F(3) \times 6!) + ((F(F(8)) - (7!)) \times 6))$
36877 := $(F(((3 + 6) + 8)) - (7! \times (-7)))$
36882 := $((3!)! + (F(F(6)) \times (F(8) \times 82)))$
36884 := $((F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - (8!/(-8))) \times 4$
36886 := $((-(((3! - 6!) \times F(8))) + F(F(8))) + F(F(F(6))))$
36892 := $(F(3) \times ((F(6)!) + ((F(F(8)) - 9) \times (-2))))$
36893 := $-((F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - ((8! + F(9)) + 3!))$
36894 := $((F(3) \times 6!) - F(8)) \times (F(9) - F((F(4)!)!))$
36896 := $(F(3!) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(8)) + (-9!)/F(F(6))))))$
36897 := $(F(F(3!)) \times ((F(F(6)) - (8 \times F(9))) \times (-7)))$
36918 := $((F(3)!)! - (F(F(6)) \times (9 \times 18)))$
36926 := $((F((3! + F(6))) \times (-9)) - F(2)) + (F(6)!)$
36927 := $((F(3) + (6))!) + (-9) \times F((2 \times 7))$
36928 := $((F((3! + F(6))) \times (-9)) + (F(2) + 8!))$
36930 := $(F(3) \times ((6! + F(9)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!))))$
36933 := $((F((3! + F(6))) \times (-9)) + (F(3)!)! + 3!)$
36936 := $((3!)! - ((6! - 9!)/(F(3) + F(6))))$
36938 := $((F(3) + 6!) \times (F(9) + F(3))) + F(F(8))$

$$\begin{aligned} 36943 &:= ((-F(3)) + (F(6))!) - (((-9) + 4!)^3)) \\ 36944 &:= (((3!)! + (F(6))!) - (F((9 - F(4)))^4)) \\ 36945 &:= (((((3!)! + F(F(6))) \times 9) + ((F(4))!)!) \times 5) \\ 36946 &:= ((F(F(3)) - (((6 + 9)^{F(4)}))) + (F(6))!) \\ 36947 &:= ((F(3!)! - (((F(6))!/(9 + F(4))) + F(7))) \\ 36948 &:= (3 - (((6 + 9)^{F(4)} - 8!)) \\ 36949 &:= (3 - ((6! + F(9)) \times (-49))) \\ 36952 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) \times (5! + F(2)))) \\ 36953 &:= ((F(F(3!)) - ((6! \times (F(9) + 5!))))/(-3)) \\ 36954 &:= -((3! - ((6! \times (F(9) + 5!))/F(4))) \\ 36955 &:= (((3!)! + (F(6))!) - (((F(9) \times 5!) + (5)))) \\ 36956 &:= ((F(3) + (F(6))!) - (F(9) \times (5! - F(F(6))))) \\ 36958 &:= -((F(3) - (((6 - F(9)) \times 5!) + 8!)) \\ 36959 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (69 \times F((5 + 9)))) \\ \\ 36960 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 0 \\ 36961 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 1 \\ 36962 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 2 \\ 36963 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 3 \\ 36964 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 4 \\ 36965 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 5 \\ 36966 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 6 \\ 36967 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 7 \\ 36968 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 8 \\ 36969 &:= F(3!)! + F(6)!/(9 - F(F(6))) + 9 \\ \\ 36972 &:= (F(3) \times (((6! - 9) \times F(7)) \times 2)) \\ 36973 &:= (((((F(3!)!)/(-F(F(6)) - 9))) + F(7)) + (F(3!)!)) \\ 36974 &:= (F(3) - (((6! - 9) \times F(7)) \times (-4))) \\ 36984 &:= (((-3) + F(6))!) + (9 \times (8^4)) \\ 36988 &:= ((F((3 + 6)) \times (-98)) + 8!) \\ 36989 &:= ((F(F(3)) + (F(6))!) + (-98) \times F(9)) \\ 36990 &:= ((F((3! + F(6))) + F(9)) \times 90) \\ 36996 &:= (3! \times (((6! - F(9)) \times 9) - F(6))) \\ 37004 &:= (((3! \times 7!) - 0!) + F((-0!) + F(F((F(4))!)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 37005** := $((3! \times 7!) + F((-0!) + F(F((0! + (5))))))$
37006 := $((3! \times 7!) + 0!) + F((-0!) + F(F(6)))$
37019 := $((3 \times F(F(7 + 0!))) + (F(19)))$
37039 := $((3! \times 7!) + F((-0!) + F(F(3!)))) + F(9)$
37047 := $((3 \times F(F(7))) \times (0! + (4 \times F(7))))$
37048 := $((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(7))) \times ((0! - 4!) - F(8)))$
37050 := $((3!)! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 50$
37058 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(7) + 0!) \times F((5 + 8))))$
37064 := $((F(3!))!/(-7 + 0!) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 4))$
37065 := $(F(F(3!)) \times ((F(F(7)) + (-((0! - (6))))!) \times 5))$
37072 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) - 0!) \times (7 \times 2)))$
37086 := $((F(3!))! - ((7 \times (0! + F(8))) \times F(F(6))))$
37097 := $((F(3)^{F(7)-0!}) \times 9) + F(F(7))$
37120 := $(F(3!) \times ((F(F(7)) - 1) \times 20))$
37126 := $((F(((3 + F(7)) + 1)) \times (-2)) + (F(6))!)$
37128 := $(F(3!) \times ((F(F(7)) - 12) \times F(8)))$
37135 := $(-((F(3!))!) - (7 \times ((1 - F(F(F(3!)))) - 5!)))$
37136 := $((F(F(3!)) + (F((F(7) + 1)))) \times (-F(3!))) + (F(6))!$
37144 := $((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) - ((1 + (F(4))!)!) + (F((F(4))!)!))$
37147 := $((F((3! + F(7))) \times (-1)) + F(4!)) - (7!)$
37154 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((7! \times (1 - 5)) + F(4!)))$
37158 := $(3 \times (((F(7) - 1) \times 5!) + F(F(8))))$
37167 := $((-(((F(3)^{F(7)} + 1)) + (F(6))!) + (7!)))$
37168 := $(-(((F(3)^{F(7)} - ((1 + 6))!) - 8!)))$
37174 := $((F(3!))! - (F(7) \times ((1 + F(F(7))) + F((F(4))!))))$
37184 := $((F(3!))! - (((7 \times 1) \times 8)^{F(F(4))}))$
37187 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) + (1 \times 8)) \times F(7)))$
37195 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(7) + ((1 - 9))^5))$
37225 := $(-(((F(3!))! - ((7!/2) + F(25))))$
37232 := $((F(3!) \times F(7)) \times (-2 - ((3!)/(-2)))$
37233 := $((F(3!))! - (7 \times (F(2^3)^{F(3)}))$
37240 := $((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) - 2) \times (F(F((F(4))!) - 0!))$
37243 := $(-(3! - (((F(7)^2) + 4!)^{F(3)}))$
37244 := $((F(3!))! + (((7^2) + ((F(4))!)!) \times (-4)))$

- 37248** := $((F(3)^7) \times (-24)) + 8!$
37252 := $((F(3)!) - (F(7) \times ((2 - 5!) \times (-2))))$
37254 := $((F(F(3!)) \times ((F(7) \times (-2)) - 5!)) + (F((F(4)!)!))$
37257 := $((F(3)!) - ((F((F(7) + 2)) \times 5) + F(7)))$
37260 := $((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) - F(2)) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)$
37264 := $((F(3!) \times (-F(7))) + (2^{F(6)})) + F(4!)$
37265 := $((F(3)!) - ((F(F(7)) + 2) \times (F(6) + (5))))$
37267 := $((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(2) + F(F(6)))) - F(7)$
37273 := $((F(3)!) - (((F(F(7)) + 2) \times F(7)) - F(3!)))$
37273 := $((F(3)!) - (((F(F(7)) + 2) \times F(7)) - F(3!)))$
37274 := $((F(3)!) - (((F(F(7)) + F(2)) \times F(7)) + 4))$
37275 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (F((F(7) + 2)) + (F(F(7)) \times 5)))$
37276 := $(-F(3) + (((F(F(7)) + F(2)) \times (-F(7))) + (F(6)!)))$
37277 := $((F(3)!) - ((7 \times 2) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7))))$
37278 := $((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times (-F(2) \times F(7))) + 8!$
- 37280** := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 0$
37281 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 1$
37282 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 2$
37283 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 3$
37284 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 4$
37285 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 5$
37286 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 6$
37287 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 7$
37288 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 8$
37289 := $F(3!) \times F(F(7)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) + 9$
- 37290** := $((F(3)!) - ((F(F(7)) \times F(-((2 - 9)))) + 0!))$
37291 := $((F(3)!) - (F(F(7)) \times F(-(((2 - 9) \times 1))))$
37292 := $((F(3)!) - ((F(F(7)) \times F(-((2 - 9)))) - F(2)))$
37293 := $((F(3)!) - ((F(F(7)) \times F(-((2 - 9)))) - F(3)))$
37294 := $((F(3!) + (F((7 \times 2)))) \times F(9)) - 4$
37295 := $((F(3!) \times 7!) - (F(2) + (9!/5!)))$
37298 := $((F(3!) + (F((7 \times 2)))) \times F((9!/8!)))$
37303 := $(-(((F(3!) \times F((7 \times F(3)))) + 0!)) + (F(3)!))$

- 37304** := $(-((F((F(3) \times 7)) - ((3! + 0!))!)) \times F((F(4))!))$
37317 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times F((1 \times 7))))$
37320 := $((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) + F(3)) \times 20$
37322 := $((((F(3!))! + F(F(7))) + (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2))) \times 2)$
37323 := $(-F((F(3) \times 7))) \times (F(F(3!)) - ((2 + 3)!))$
37324 := $((-3) + (F(7) \times ((3!)! - 2))) \times 4$
37328 := $(F(3) \times ((F(F(7)) + 3!!) + F((F(2) + F(8))))$
37329 := $((F(3!))! - ((F((7 + 3))^2) - F(9)))$
37330 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) - 3) \times F((3! + 0!))))$
37334 := $(-F(3) - (F(7) \times ((3!)! - F(3)) \times (-4)))$
37335 := $((F(3!))! - ((-F(7)) + F((-3!) + F(F(3!)))) \times 5)$
37336 := $((3 - F((7 + 3))) \times (F(3) - 6!))$
37337 := $(-F(F(3))) + (((F(F(7)) + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(3!))) \times 7)$
37338 := $((3!)! + ((F(7)^{F(3)})) \times (F(3) \times F(8)))$
37339 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + 7) \times 3 - ((F(3!))! / (-9)))$
37340 := $((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) + 3) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!)$
37343 := $((F(3!))! - (F(F(7)) + ((F(3!) + (F(4))!)^3)))$
37345 := $((F(3)^{F(7)} - 3!!) - F(4)) \times 5$
37347 := $(-((F(3) - ((F(7)^3) \times (4! - 7))))$
37348 := $(F(3) \times ((F(((7 - 3)!)) / (F(4))!) + F(F(8))))$
37349 := $((3! + 7)^3 \times (F((F(4))!) + 9))$
37353 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (-7)) \times F(F(3!)) + 5!) + (F(3!))!$
37354 := $((F(3)^{F(7)} - 3!!) \times 5) - (F(4))!$
37355 := $((F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times (35 + 5!))$
37356 := $((F(3) \times F(7)) \times (3! - 5!)) + (F(6))!$
37357 := $((F(3!))! + (((F(7)^3) - 5!) - 7!))$
37359 := $((F((3! + F(7))) + (3! \times (-5))) \times 9)$
37360 := $((F(3)^{F(7)} - 3!!) \times (6 - 0!))$
37362 := $((F(3) \times F(7)) \times (-3) + (6! \times 2))$
37363 := $((F(3!))! - (((-7!) + F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) / F(3))$
37364 := $(F(3) - (F(7) \times (3! + (6! \times (-4))))$
37365 := $((F(3)^{F(7)} + F(F(3))) - (6!)) \times 5$
37366 := $(-((F(3) \times ((F(7)^3) - 6!))) + (F(6))!$
37367 := $((F(F(F(3!))) + 7!) / (-F(3))) + (((F(6))! + 7!))$

- 37368** := $((-(3) \times 7!) - (3^{F(6)} \times (-8)))$
37369 := $-((((3!)! + (F(7)^3)) - (F(6))! + F(9)))$
37370 := $((F(3))! - (((F(F(7)) - 3!) \times F(7)) - 0!))$
37373 := $((((F(F(F(3!))) \times (-7)) / (F(3) \times F(7))) + (F(3))!))$
37373 := $((((F(F(F(3!))) \times (-7)) / (F(3) \times F(7))) + (F(3))!))$
37374 := $((((F(3))! - ((F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times F(7))) - F(F((F(4))!)))$
37377 := $((((3 \times F(F(7))) \times 3) - (7! \times (-7)))$
37379 := $((((-3!) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(3))) \times F(F(7))) + 9!$
37380 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (F((F(7) - F(3))) \times (F(8) - 0!)))$
37383 := $((3!)! + F(7)) \times ((3! \times 8) + 3)$
37384 := $(F(3!) + (73 \times (8^{F(4)})))$
37385 := $((3!)! + (F(F(7)) \times (F(3!) + (F(8)))) \times 5)$
37386 := $((-3!) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(3)^8))) + (F(6))!$
37388 := $((((F(F(F(3!))) - 7!) / (-F(3))) + ((8! + F(8))))$
37389 := $((((3!)! - F(F(7))) \times (-3!)) + ((8! - 9)))$
37393 := $((F(3))! - ((7^3) + F((9 \times F(3))))$
37394 := $((F(3))! - ((F(7)^3) + (9^{F(4)})))$
37396 := $((((F(3!) + ((F(7) \times 3!))) \times (-F(9))) + (F(6))!))$
37397 := $(F(F(3)) + ((F((F(7) + 3!)) \times 9) - F(F(7))))$
37398 := $((((3!)! - F(F(7))) \times (3 - 9)) + 8!)$
37402 := $(3! - ((F(F(7)) - F((4! + 0!))) / 2))$
37403 := $((F(3))! - ((F(7)^{F(4)} + ((03))!))$
37404 := $(F(3!) - ((F(F(7)) - F((4! + 0!))) / F(F(4))))$
37406 := $((3!)! \times (F(7) \times 4) - F((0! + F(6))))$
37412 := $((((3!)! + 7) \times (-4)) + (F(((1 + 2))!))!)$
37413 := $((F((3! + F(7))) - (4!)) \times (1 + F(3!)))$
37414 := $((F(3) \times F(7)) \times (((F(4))! - 1) + ((F(4))!))$
37415 := $((F(3))! - (7 \times 415))$
37416 := $((-((3^7) + F(4!)) - F((-1 + F(F(6))))$
37418 := $((3!)! \times (F(7) \times 4) - (1 + F(8)))$
37419 := $((3!)! \times (F(7) \times 4) - F(-((1 - 9))))$
37420 := $((3!)! \times (F(7) \times 4) - (20))$
37422 := $((F(F(3!)) + (7! / F(4))) \times 22)$
37423 := $((F(3))! - (F(7) + (4 \times (F(2) + 3!))))$

- 37424** := (((3!)! × F(7)) − 4) × (F(2) + F(4))
37425 := ((3 − (F(7) × (4!²))) × (−5))
37426 := (F(3) × (−(7) + ((4! + 2) × 6!)))
37427 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) − (F(2) × F(7)))
37428 := (((F(3!) + F(F(7))) × (4!/−2))) + 8!)
37429 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) − (2 + 9))
37430 := (3 + (F(7) × ((4 × (3!)!) − 0!)))
37431 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) − F(3!)) − 1
37432 := (((3!)! × F(7)) − F(F(4))) × (F(3) + 2))
37433 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) − 3!) − F(F(3))
37434 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) − (F(3) + (4)))
37435 := (((3!)! × ((F(7) × 4!)/3!)) − (5))
37436 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + ((F(3) − (6))))
37437 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) − F(−((3 − 7))))
37438 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + ((3! − 8)))
37440 := (((3 × F(7)) × 4!) × 40)
37441 := (F(F(3)) + (((F(7) × 4!) × ((4 + 1)!)))
37442 := (F(3) + ((F(7) × 4) × ((4 + 2)!))
37443 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + F((4!/3!)))
37444 := (((3!)! × F(7)) + (4/4)) × 4
37445 := ((F(F(3)) + (((F(7) × 4!) × 4!))) × 5)
37448 := (((3!)! × F(7)) + F(F(4))) × (−(4 − 8))
37449 := ((F((3! + F(7))) − (4! − (4))) × 9)
37450 := (−(3) + (F(7) × ((4! × 5!) + 0!)))
37451 := −((F(3) − (F(7) × ((4! × 5!) + 1))))
37452 := (3! × (((F(7) × 4) × 5!) + 2))
37453 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + F((5 + F(3))))
37454 := ((F(3!) + ((F(7) × 4!) × 5!)) + (F(4)!))
37455 := ((−(3!) + F(F(7))) × (F(4) × 55))
37456 := (((F(3) × (7⁴)) − 5!) × F(6))
37458 := (F(3) × (((F(7) − (4))⁵) − 8!))
37460 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + F(F(6))) − 0!
37461 := (F(3!) − (F(7) × ((−(4) × 6!) − 1)))
37462 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + F(F(6))) + F(2))
37463 := (−(3) + (F(7) × ((4 × 6!) + F(3))))

- 37465** := (((-(F(3)) - F(F(7))) + (F(4!)/6)) × 5)
37466 := (((F(3) × F(7)) + (-4 × 6!)) + (F(6)!))
37467 := ((3^{F(7)-F(4)!}) + ((F(6))! - (7!)))
37469 := ((F(3!))! - (7 + (4 × (6! - 9))))
37471 := (((3!)! - F(7)) × ((4 × F(7)) + 1))
37472 := (F(3!) × (7! - (4 × F((F(7) - 2))))))
37473 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(7) × F(4)) × 73))
37474 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + F((F(7) - (4))))
37475 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + (7 × 5))
37476 := (((F(F(3)) - F(7)) × (4 + F(F(7)))) + (F(6)!))
37477 := (((3! + (7))^{F(4)}) - (7! × (-7)))
37478 := (F(F(3)) + (((F(7)^{F(4)}) - 7!) + 8!))
37479 := -((((F(3!) - (F(7)^{F(4)})) × F(F(7))) + F(9))
37482 := (((3!)! × (F(7) × 4)) + (F(8) × 2))
37484 := ((F((F(3) × 7)) + F(4!)) - (F(8)^{F(4)}))
37486 := (((3!)! - F(7)) × (-4)) + ((8! - (6)))
37488 := (((3 + F(F(7))) × (-4 + 8)) + 8!)
37492 := (((3!)! - F(7)) × (-4)) + ((9 - F(2)))!
37493 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) + (4!)) × (9 + F(3))))
37494 := -((3! × ((F(7) × 4!) - (9⁴)))
37496 := -(((F(3!) × (F(F(7)) + (-((4 - 9))))!) - (F(6)!))
37497 := ((F((3 + 7)) × (((F(4))!)! - F(9))) - F(F(7)))
37498 := (((3! - F((7 + 4))) × F(9)) + 8!)
37499 := (((3!)! - F(F(7))) × (-4 - (9 × 9)))
37503 := ((F(3!))! - (F(F(7)) + F(((5 + 0!) × 3))))
37504 := ((F(3!))! + (-((F(F(7)) + ((5! - 0!))) × F((F(4))!)))
37506 := ((F(3!))! - (((F(7) + 5!) + 0!) × F(F(6))))
37518 := (3 × ((F(7) × 5!) + F(F((1 × 8))))))
37522 := (((3! + F(7)) + F((5²)))/2)
37524 := (F(3!) + ((7 + F((5²)))/F(F(4))))
37526 := ((F(3!))! - ((-7 - 5!) × (-F(2) - F(F(6))))))
37527 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(7) + 5!) × F((F(2) + (7))))))
37528 := ((F(F(3!)) × (-F(7) + 5!)) + ((F(2) + 8!)))
37533 := (((F(F(3!)) × (-F(7) + 5!)) + (F(3!))!) + 3!)

- 37534** := (((3! × F(F(7))) − (5)) × (−F(3))) + (F((F(4))!))!
37536 := (3 × (((F(7) × 5!) + 3!) + F(F(F(6))))))
37539 := ((F((3! + F(7))) − (5 × F(3))) × 9)
37542 := (((F(F(F(3!))) − (F(7) × 5!)) × 4) − 2)
37543 := −((F(F(3)) − (F(7) × ((5! × 4!) + F(3!))))))
37544 := (F(3!) + (((F(7) × 5!) + (4)) × 4!))
37546 := (F(3) + (F(7) × ((5! × 4!) + F(6))))
37548 := ((F(3!))! − ((7 + (5^{F(4)})) × F(8)))
37549 := −((F(3!) − ((F(7) × ((5! × 4!) + 9))))))
37553 := ((F(3!))! + ((F(F(7)) − (5! × (5^{F(3)}))))))
37554 := −((3! − (((F(7) × 5!) + (5)) × 4!))
37557 := (((−(F(3)) + F(F(7))) + 5!) × (5! − F(7)))
37563 := (((F(F(3!)) × 75) + F(F(F(6)))) × 3)
37564 := ((F(3!))! − (F(F(7)) + ((5! × F(F(6))) + F(4))))
37566 := −(((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) − ((−(5!) × F(F(6))) + (F(6))!)))
37567 := (((F(3) + F(7)) × 5!) × F(F(6))) − F(F(7))
37568 := (F(3!) × (((F(7) + 5!) − 6!) × (−8)))
37571 := −(((F(3!))! + ((F(F(7)) − ((5⁷) − 1))))))
37572 := ((F(3!))! − (F(F(7)) + (−(5) − (7!/−2))))
37573 := (((F(F(3)) − F(F(7))) + (5⁷)) − (F(3!))!)
37573 := (((F(F(3)) − F(F(7))) + (5⁷)) − (F(3!))!)
37574 := −(((F(3!))! + ((F(F(7)) − (5⁷)) − F(F(4))))))
37577 := ((F(3!))! − (F(7) × (5! − (−(7) × F(7))))))
37578 := ((3! − F(F(7))) − (−(5⁷) + 8!))
37584 := ((3! + (F(7) × 5!)) × ((8 − 4)!))
37586 := (((3! − (7! × (−5))) + F(F(8))) + (6!))
37588 := ((F(3!))! − (F(F(7)) + ((5! × F(8)) − F(8))))
37590 := ((F(3!))! − (F(7) × (5! + (90))))
37592 := ((F(3!))! − (F((7 + 5)) + F((9 × 2))))
37597 := (((F((3! + F(7))) − (5)) × 9) + F(7))
37598 := −(((3! + (((F(7) × (5! + F(9))) − 8!))))
37608 := ((F((3! + F(7))) × (F(6) + 0!)) − (F(8)))
37620 := ((F(3) + (7)) × (F((F(F(6)) − 2)) − 0!))
37624 := ((F(3!))! − ((F(F(7)) + (F(F(6))²)) × 4))

$$\begin{aligned}
 37626 &:= (- (3!) + ((7 \times F(F(6))) \times (2^{F(6)}))) \\
 37630 &:= ((F((3! + F(7))) \times (6 + 3)) + 0!) \\
 37631 &:= (F(3) + (F((F(7) + (6))) \times (F(3!) + 1))) \\
 37633 &:= (F(F(3)) - ((- (7) \times F(F(6))) \times (F(3)^{F(3!)}))) \\
 37634 &:= (((- ((F(3)^7)) \times F(F(6))) + (F(3!)!) + F(F(4))) \\
 37637 &:= (F(3!) + (F((F(7) + (6))) \times (F(3) + (7)))) \\
 37638 &:= ((- ((F(3)^7)) \times F(F(6))) + (3! + 8!)) \\
 37644 &:= ((F(F(3)) - ((F(7) \times (6! + (4)))) \times (-4)) \\
 37645 &:= ((F(3!)! - (- (F(7)) - ((F(6))! / (F(4) \times (-5)))) \\
 37646 &:= (((- (F(3)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6))!) - (F(4!) / F(F(6)))) \\
 37652 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - (F(F(7)) + (6! \times 52))) \\
 37653 &:= 3 \times (7 + (F(6) - 5!)^{F(3)}) \\
 37656 &:= (((3^7) + (F(F(6)) \times 5!)) \times F(6)) \\
 37658 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - F(F(7))) \times (- (6) - 5!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 37659 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - (7! + ((F(6) \times 5!) \times F(9)))) \\
 37661 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7))) + ((F(6)^{6-1})) \\
 37664 &:= (((3!)! \times F(7)) + ((F(6))! / 6!)) \times 4) \\
 37672 &:= ((- ((F(3)^7)) + (F(6))!) + (7! / (-2))) \\
 37673 &:= ((F(3!)! - (((- (7!) - F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) / (-F(3)))) \\
 37673 &:= ((F(3!)! - (((- (7!) - F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) / (-F(3)))) \\
 37674 &:= ((F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) + ((6! \times F(7)) \times 4)) \\
 37675 &:= (F((3 + 7)) \times (6! - (7 \times 5))) \\
 37678 &:= (- (3) - ((7 \times F((F(F(6)) - 7))) - 8!)) \\
 37680 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((7 \times F((6 + 8))) + 0!)) \\
 37681 &:= ((F(3!)! - (7 \times F(((6 + 8) \times 1)))) \\
 37682 &:= ((- (3!) + F(F(7))) \times ((F(6) \times F(8)) - 2)) \\
 37687 &:= (((3^7) + 6!) - 8) \times F(7) \\
 37688 &:= -(((3!)! - (((F(F(7)) + 6) \times (-8)) + 8!)) \\
 37693 &:= (((F(3!) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \times 9) - F(3!)) \\
 37694 &:= (- (((F(3) \times (7! - 6!)) + F(9))) + F(4!)) \\
 37695 &:= (((3! - F((F(7) + (6)))) \times (-9)) + 5!) \\
 37696 &:= ((F(3!) \times (7 \times (6! - F(9)))) - (6!)) \\
 37697 &:= ((F(3!) \times (F(F(7)) - ((F(6))! / (-9)))) - 7) \\
 37698 &:= ((3 \times ((7! / (-6)) - F(9))) + 8!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 37699 &:= ((-(37) + (F(6))!) - F((9 + 9))) \\
 37713 &:= ((F((F(3) \times 7)) \times 71) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 37723 &:= ((F(3!))! - (7 \times (F((7 \times 2) - 3!))) \\
 37724 &:= (((3 + F(F(7))) \times (-F(7) - 2)) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 37725 &:= ((F(3) + F(7)) \times ((7!/2) - (5))) \\
 37729 &:= ((F(3!) \times 7!) - (7 + F((2 \times 9)))) \\
 37730 &:= (((F(F(F(3!))) + (7 \times F(F(7)))) \times 3) - 0!) \\
 37731 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) + (7 \times F(F(7)))) \times (3 \times 1)) \\
 37732 &:= (((F(3!))! + (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7)))) + (F(F(3!))²)) \\
 37733 &:= (-3) + (((7! - F(F(7))) \times F(3!)) - 3!!) \\
 37734 &:= ((F(3!) \times (7! - F(F(7)))) - ((3!)! + F(F(4)))) \\
 37735 &:= (((F(3!))! - F(F(7))) + ((-7) \times (F(3!))!)/5!) \\
 37736 &:= ((F(3!) \times 7!) - F((F((7 - 3)) \times 6))) \\
 37737 &:= ((F(3!) + ((7! + (7³)))) \times 7) \\
 37738 &:= ((F(3) - F(((7) + F(7)) \times 3)) + 8!) \\
 37739 &:= (F((3! + F(7))) + (F((F(7) + 3)) \times F(9))) \\
 37743 &:= (((F(3!) \times 7!) + 7) - F((4! - 3!))) \\
 37744 &:= (((-(37) \times F(F(7))) + F(4!)) - F(4)) \\
 37745 &:= -((F(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times ((-7) \times (F(4))! - 5!)))) \\
 37749 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-F(7) + F((F(7) - ((4 - 9)))))) \\
 37750 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((-F(7) + F((F(7) + (5)))) - 0!)) \\
 37751 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - ((5 - 1)!)))) \\
 37753 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(7) - ((7! + 5!)/F(3)))))) \\
 37754 &:= (F(3) + ((F(7) + (F(7) \times 5!)) \times 4!)) \\
 37757 &:= (((F(3) - F(7)) \times F(F(7))) + ((-5) + F(7)))! \\
 37758 &:= (((3! - 7!) \times (-7)) + (5! \times F(8))) \\
 37762 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((7! + 76)/2)) \\
 37763 &:= (((F(3) - F(7)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6))! + 3!) \\
 37764 &:= (3! \times (((F(F(7)) + F(7)) - (F(6))! + F(4!))) \\
 37768 &:= -((((3!)! - (7!)) - (F((F(7) + (6))) \times 8)) \\
 37772 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(7) \times ((7 + 7)²))) \\
 37774 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(7) + F(7)) - (-7!)/F(F(4)))) \\
 37778 &:= ((3!)! + ((F(F(7)) \times (-7 + 7)) + 8!)) \\
 37779 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (7 \times (F(F(7)) + ((F(7) - 9)!))) \\
 37782 &:= (((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(7))) + (7!)) \times (8 + F(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 37783** := $((3!^7) - F(F(7))) - ((8! \times 3!))$
37784 := $(F(3!) \times ((7! - F(F(7))) - 84))$
37786 := $-(((F(3!))! + (-7) \times ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))))))$
37787 := $((F(3!))! - (F(7) + (7!/F((F(8)/7))))))$
37792 := $((F(3!) \times (7! + (7))) - F((9 \times 2)))$
37793 := $((F(3!))! - (7 + (7!/F((9/3))))))$
37794 := $-(((3! + 7!) + ((7! \times F(9))/(-4))))$
37795 := $((F(3!))! - ((7!/(-7-9)) + (5)))$
37796 := $(((-((F(3) - (7)))^7) - 9) - (F(6))!)$
37798 := $-((F(3) + ((7!/(-7-9)) - 8!)))$
37800 := $((F(3!))! - (7!/(((8 \times 0)! + 0!)))$
37804 := $((((3!)! + 7) \times F((8 - 0!))) \times 4)$
37806 := $(-((F(3) - 7!) + (8^{-0!+6})))$
37807 := $((F(3)^{7+8} - 0!) + 7!)$
37808 := $((((F(3!) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) + 0!) \times 8)$
37809 := $((F((3! + F(7))) + (F(8) - 0!)) \times 9)$
37813 := $((F(3!))! + ((F(7) - (((8 - 1)!/F(3))))))$
37816 := $(F(3!) + (7! + (8^{-1+6})))$
37818 := $((F((3! + F(7))) + (F(8))) \times (1 + 8))$
37824 := $(F(3!) \times (7! - (F((8 - F(2))) \times 4!)))$
37826 := $((((3!)! + F(F(7))) \times 82) - (F(6))!)$
37829 := $-(((3!)! - (7 \times ((F(F(8))/2) + F(9))))))$
37832 := $((F(3!))! - ((7! - (8^{F(3)}))/2))$
37833 := $((((F(3!))! + (7 + F(F(8)))) - ((F(3!))!/3))$
37834 := $((3!)! - (-7) + (F(8)^3)) + F(4!))$
37835 := $((3! + 7!) + F(8) + (F(3!)^5))$
37836 := $-((F(F(3!)) - (7! + ((F(F(8)) \times 3) - F(F(6))))))$
37837 := $(-F(3) - (((-F(7) + F(F(8))) \times (-3)) - (7!)))$
37839 := $((3 \times (-F(7) + F(F(8)))) + (-((F(3) - 9)))!)$
37842 := $((F(3!))! - ((7! - (84))/2))$
37843 := $((F(3!))! - ((7! + F(8)) - F((4! - 3!))))$
37844 := $((-3) + (F(7) \times (8 + ((F(4))!))) \times 4)$
37845 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) - 8) \times ((F(4))! + (5))))$
37846 := $((-((F(3!) \times F(F(7)))) - F((F(8) - (F(4))!))) + (F(6))!)$
37847 := $(F(3!) + (((-F(7) + F(F(8))) \times F(4)) + (7!)))$

- 37848** := (((F(3!) - F(F(7))) × (-F(8))) + (F(4)!) × 8)
37856 := (-((F((3 + 7) + 8) - 5!)) + (F(6)!)
37857 := (((F(F(F(3!))) - 7) × (8 - 5)) + (7!))
37860 := ((F(F(3)) - (7!/(-8))) × 60)
37862 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (7! - ((F(F(8)) - F(6)) × (-2))))
37863 := (((-((F(3)⁷)) + F(F(8))) × F(F(6)))/3!)
37864 := ((F(3) - (F(7) × (-8) - 6!)) × 4)
37865 := ((F(3)!)! + ((F(F(7)) - ((8! × F(6))/5!)))
37867 := -(((F(3!) - F((7 + F(8)))) + (6⁷))
37869 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (((7! + F(F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 9))
37872 := ((F(3)!)! - ((F(7) + F(8)) × 72))
37873 := ((-((3!⁷)) + F((F(8) + (7)))) - F(3))
37873 := ((-((3!⁷)) + F((F(8) + (7)))) - F(3))
37874 := ((3 × F((F(7) + 8))) + ((7! - (4))))
37876 := (-((F(3) - 7!)) + ((F(8)/7) × F(F(F(6))))))
37877 := ((-((3! - 7!)) + F((F(8) - (7)))) × 7)
37878 := (((F(3) × F((F(7) + 8))) + (7!)) + F(F(8)))
37879 := ((F(F(3)) + (7!)) + (F(F(8)) × F((F(7) - 9))))
37883 := (((-3) + 7!) + 8) + (F(F(8)) × 3)
37886 := (((F(3!) + (7!)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(8))) + F(F(F(6))))
37888 := (((3!)! × (-F(7))) - ((F(F(8)) × (-8)) + 8!))
37889 := ((F(3)!)! - (((F(7) - F(F(8))) - F(F(8)))/(-9)))
37896 := (-(((3!⁷) - F(8))) + F((F(9) - (6))))
37899 := ((F((3! + F(7))) + (F(8) + 9)) × 9)
37917 := ((3 × (F(7) + F(F((9 - 1)))))) + (7!))
37926 := (3! × ((F(F(7)) - (F(9) × (-2))) × F(F(6))))
37928 := (((F(3) × F(7)) × (-92)) + 8!)
37932 := ((F(3)!)! - ((F(F(7)) - F(9)) × (3! × 2)))
37933 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (-F(7) + ((9 + F(F(3!)))³)))
37934 := (((F(F(F(3!))) × 7) - (F(9) + 3!))/F(F(4)))
37935 := ((F(3) + F(7)) × (9 - (F(F(3!)) × (-5!))))
37936 := ((F(3)!)! - (F(F(7)) + (-9 - (-3) × 6!)))
37938 := (3! × ((-7) × F(9)) + (3⁸))
37944 := (((3!)! × (7 + F(9))) + F(4!))/F(F(4))
37947 := (F(F(3!)) × ((F(F(7)) - 94) × F(7)))

- 37948** := (((((F(3!))! + F(F(7))) - F((9 × F(F(4)))))) - (F(8)))
37954 := (((F(3!) × F(F(7))) × (-9)) + (5 × F(F(F((F(4)!))))))
37960 := (((F(3!) × F(F(7))) + F(9)) × (F(F(6)) - 0!))
37965 := ((F((3! + F(7))) × 9) - ((F(6)!)/(-5!)))
37967 := ((F(3!))! - (F(7) × (F(9) + (F(F(6)) × 7))))
37968 := (F(3!) × (-7) × ((F(9) - 6!) + 8))
37969 := ((F(3!))! + ((F(F(7)) - F((F((9 - 6)) × 9))))))
37972 := ((F(3!))! - (F(F(7)) + (9 × (F(F(7)) + 2))))
37973 := (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(7) × 9) × (F(F(7)) - F(3))))
37973 := (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(7) × 9) × (F(F(7)) - F(3))))
37974 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(F(7)) × ((9 × F(7)) - F(F(F(4))))))
37977 := ((F(3!))! - (((F(F(7)) × 9) + F(7)) + F(F(7))))
37979 := ((3 × (-7!) + F((9 + F(7)))) - F(9))
37980 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(7) × 9) × (F(8) - 0!)))
37983 := (((3!)! × F(7)) - F(9)) + F((F(8) + F(3)))
37984 := -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((7! × F((F(9) - F(8))))/4!))
37986 := (((3!)! - F(F(7))) × ((9 × 8) + 6))
37987 := (-3) - (((F(F(7)) × 9) - 8!) + F(F(7)))
37990 := ((F(3!))! - (F(F(7)) × (9 + ((9 × 0)!)))
37992 := (3! × (7! - (F((9 + 9))/(-2))))
37994 := ((F(3!))! - ((7 + (F(9) × F(9))) × F(F(4))))
38006 := ((3 × F((F(8) - 0!))) + F((0! + F(F(6))))))
38013 := (3 × (F((F(8) + 0!)) - ((1 + 3!)!))
38016 := (-(((3! × 8)^{0!+1})) + (F(6))!)
38024 := (-(((3!)! + (F(F(8))/(0 - 2)))) × F((F(4)!))
38037 := (3 × ((F((F(8) + 0!)) + F(3!)) - (7!)))
38044 := (((F(3!))! - (F((F(8) - 0!))/F(4))) - F(F((F(4)!)))
38058 := ((-3!) × F(((8 + 0!) + (5)))) + 8!
38063 := ((F(3!))! - ((F((F(8) - 0!)) + 6)/3))
38064 := ((-(((3!)! × F((8 - 0!)))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 4!)
38065 := ((F(3!))! - (F((F(8) - 0!))/(F(6) - (5))))
38074 := -((((F(F(3)) + (F(8))) × F((0! + F(7)))) - F(4!))
38076 := (3 × ((F((F(8) + 0!)) - (7!)) + F(F(6))))
38077 := ((F(F(3!)) + (80)) × F((7 + 7)))
38106 := ((F(3!))! - ((F((F(8) + 1)) + 0!)/F(6)))

$$\begin{aligned} 38115 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(8)^{1+1}) \times 5)) \\ 38123 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(((8+1)-2))^3)) \\ 38131 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(F(8)) - 1)/(3! - 1))) \\ 38132 &:= ((-((3^{8-1})) + (F(3!))!) - F(2)) \\ 38133 &:= (-((3^{8-1})) + (F((3+3)))!) \\ 38134 &:= ((-((3^{8-1})) + (F(3!))!) + F(F(F(4)))) \\ 38135 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(F(8)) - F(F(((1 \times 3)!))))/5)) \\ 38136 &:= (F(3!) \times (F(8) \times (F(13) - (6)))) \\ 38144 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F((8+1)) \times (4^{F(4)}))) \\ 38145 &:= ((3!)! + ((F((F(8) - 1)) + ((F(4)!))!) \times 5)) \\ 38146 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-F((8+1))) + (F(4!)/F(F(6)))) \\ 38154 &:= -(((3! - 8!) + (((1+5)! \times F(4)))) \\ 38155 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(F(8)) + (-1 - 5!))/5)) \\ 38164 &:= (((3+8!) + 1) - (6! \times F(4))) \\ 38167 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((8!/F(F((1 \times 6)))) + F(F(7)))) \\ 38169 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(F((8-1))) + 6) \times 9)) \\ 38178 &:= (((3! \times F(8)) \times (-17)) + 8!) \\ 38184 &:= -(((3! - F((8+1)+8))) \times 4!) \\ 38196 &:= (((3 + F(F((8-1)))) \times (-9)) + (F(6))!) \\ 38198 &:= (((F(3) - 8!)/19) + 8!) \\ 38213 &:= (-((F(3) - F((8+2)))) \times (1 + 3!!)) \\ 38223 &:= (((3!)! - (F(8))) \times (-2 - F(2))) + (F(3!))! \\ 38227 &:= (((F(F(F(3!))) - ((8/2)!)/2) \times 7) \\ 38228 &:= (((-3) - F((F(8) - 2)))/2) + 8! \\ 38231 &:= (((3!)! + 8!)/2) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1)) \\ 38234 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - (F(F(8)) - F(2))) \times F(F(3!)))/(-F(4)!)) \\ 38235 &:= ((-3!) - (F(F(8)))/(-2)) + (F(3!)^5) \\ 38239 &:= (F(-((3! - F(8)))) - (F((-2) + F(F(3!)))) \times (-9)) \\ 38243 &:= ((3!)! + ((F(8) + F((F(2) + 4!)))/F(3))) \\ 38244 &:= -((((3!)!/8)^2) + (4!)) - F(4!) \\ 38245 &:= (((F(3!) + F(F(8)))/2) + (F((F(4)!))^5)) \\ 38247 &:= (-F(3!) + (((F(F(8)))/(-2)) + F((F(4)!)) \times (-7))) \\ 38253 &:= (-((3^{8-F(2)}) - 5!) + (F(3!))!) \\ 38254 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (82 \times (-5!) + ((F(4)!))!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38259 &:= ((3! - F((8 \times 2))) \times (-5 - F(9))) \\
 38262 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (((F(F(8)) - 2)/6) - 2)) \\
 38264 &:= -((F(3!) - (8! - (2^{F(6)+F(4)})))) \\
 38266 &:= -(((3! - 8!) + ((2^{F(6)}) \times F(6)))) \\
 38268 &:= ((-38) \times (F(2) - 6!)) + F(F(8)) \\
 38270 &:= (((3! + (F(F(8)))/(-2))) \times (-7)) + 0! \\
 38272 &:= (F(F(3)) \times (8! - (2^{F(7)-2}))) \\
 38273 &:= (F(F(3)) + (8! - (2^{F(7)-F(3)}))) \\
 38274 &:= ((F(3) + 8!) - (2^{7+4})) \\
 38277 &:= ((((-3!) + F(F(8)))/(-2)) \times (-7)) - F(7) \\
 38280 &:= ((F(3!))! - (8 \times ((2^8) - 0!))) \\
 38283 &:= (((F(3!) - F(F(8)))/2) \times (F(8)/(-3))) \\
 38283 &:= (((F(3!) - F(F(8)))/2) \times (F(8)/(-3))) \\
 38288 &:= (((F(3)^8) - 2) \times (-8)) + 8! \\
 38293 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(8) - (2^{9+F(3)})))) \\
 38294 &:= ((3! - 8!) - (-2) \times (F(9)^{F(4)})) \\
 38296 &:= (F(3!) \times ((F(F(8))/2) + (F(9) - 6!))) \\
 38302 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((8!/(F(F(3!)) - 0!)) + 2)) \\
 38303 &:= -((F(3!) - ((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) \times (-0! + 3!))) \\
 38304 &:= ((3! \times F(8)) \times 304) \\
 38305 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8)))/3!) - (0! + 5)) \\
 38306 &:= ((38 \times (3!))! + F(F(F(06)))) \\
 38307 &:= (3 + (((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) + 0!) \times (-7)) \\
 38308 &:= (-3) + ((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) \times (0! - 8) \\
 \\
 38310 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 0 \\
 38311 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 1 \\
 38312 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 2 \\
 38313 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 3 \\
 38314 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 4 \\
 38315 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 5 \\
 38316 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 6 \\
 38317 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 7 \\
 38318 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38319 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))/3! - 1 + 9 \\ 38323 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8)))/3!) + (2 \times 3!)) \\ 38324 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8)))/3!) + F((F(2) + (F(4)!))) \\ 38326 &:= (F(3!) - ((F(8) \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 2))/(-6))) \\ 38329 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8)))/3!) + (2 \times 9)) \\ 38331 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(8)) + 3!))/3!) - 1) \\ 38332 &:= (((3! + F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) \times (- (3! + F(2)))) \\ 38333 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times (- (F(F(8)) + 3!)) - 3!)/(-3!)) \\ 38334 &:= (3! + (F((8 + (3 \times 3))) \times 4!)) \\ 38335 &:= (((3!)! - (F(8) + F(3))) \times F((F(3) \times 5))) \\ 38336 &:= (((-(F(3)^8) + F(3!)) \times F(3!)) + (F(6)!)) \\ 38337 &:= (- (F(3)) + (((F(F(8)) + F(3!))/(-F(3))) \times (-7))) \\ 38338 &:= (((-(F(3)) \times F((8 \times F(3)))) - F(3!)) + 8!) \\ 38339 &:= (((F(3!) + F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) \times (F(3) - 9)) \\ 38340 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(8)) + F(3!)))/F(4)!)) + 0! \\ 38342 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((F((8 \times F(3))) + F(F(4))) \times 2)) \\ 38343 &:= ((- (3) + 8!) - (F(3) \times F((4^{F(3)})))) \\ 38344 &:= -(((F(3) - 8!) + (F(3) \times F((4 \times 4)))) \\ 38345 &:= (((((F(3!)!)/(-F(8))) + (F(3!)!)) - F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\ 38346 &:= (((((F(3!) - F(F(8)))/(-3!)) + F(4)) \times F(F(6))) \\ 38347 &:= (F(3!) + (((F(F(8)))/(-F(3))) - 4) \times (-7)) \\ 38348 &:= (((-(F(3)) \times F((8 \times F(3)))) + F(F(4))) + 8!) \\ 38349 &:= ((3!)! + (F((8 \times F(3)) + F(4))) \times 9)) \\ 38350 &:= (((((F(3!)!)/(-F(8))) + (F(3!)!)) - 50) \\ 38352 &:= ((F(3!)! - (8 \times ((- (3) - 5!) \times (-2)))) \\ 38353 &:= ((- (3!) + (F(F(8)))/(-F(3)))) \times (- (5) - F(3)) \\ 38354 &:= ((F(3!) + 8!) - (F((F(F(3!)) - 5))) \times F(F(4))) \\ 38356 &:= (((- (F(3)) \times (F((8 \times F(3))) - 5))) + (F(6)!)) \\ 38358 &:= ((F(3) \times (- (F(8)) + (F(3!) \times (-5!)))) + 8!) \\ 38360 &:= (((((F(3!)!)/F(8)) - F(3)) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)) \\ 38362 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((- (8) + F((F(3) \times F(6)))) \times 2)) \\ 38364 &:= (((((F(3!)!)/(-F(8))) + (F(3!)!)) - (6^{F(F(4))})) \\ 38366 &:= (((((3! - 8!) - 3!)/F(F(6))) + (F(6)!)) \\ 38367 &:= (((((3 \times F(F(8)))/3!) + F(6)) \times 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38369 &:= (((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) - ((-3) - (F(6))!) + F(9)) \\
 38372 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(8) + 3!) + F(F(7))) \times 2)) \\
 38373 &:= (((F(3!) - (F(F(8)) / (-F(3)))) \times 7) + 3!) \\
 38375 &:= (((F(3!) + (F(F(8)) / (-F(3)))) \times (-7)) + 5!) \\
 38376 &:= ((-((3^{8-3}) + 7!) \times F(6)) \\
 38379 &:= (((3^8) \times 3!) - F((7 + 9))) \\
 38380 &:= (((((F(3!))! / F(8)) - F(F(3))) \times (F(8) - 0!)) \\
 38383 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) + ((F(3!) \times F((F(8) - 3)))))) \\
 38383 &:= (F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) + ((F(3!) \times F((F(8) - 3)))))) \\
 38384 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(8) + F(3)) + F(8))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 38386 &:= ((-((3! - 8!) - F(3!)) - (8! / F(F(6)))) \\
 38387 &:= (((3!)! \times (-8)) / 3) + ((8! - F(7))) \\
 38388 &:= ((F((3 \times 8)) / (-3 \times 8)) + 8!) \\
 38389 &:= (((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) - ((F(3) - 8!) + 9)) \\
 38390 &:= (((3!)! - (F(8))) - F(F(3))) \times F((9 + 0!)) \\
 38391 &:= (((((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) + (F(3!))!) - (9 \times 1)) \\
 38392 &:= (F(3!) \times (8 + (3 \times F((F(9) / 2)))))) \\
 38393 &:= (((((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) + (F(3!))!) - (9 - F(3))) \\
 38394 &:= (((((F(F(3)) + 8) - 3!) \times (-9)) \times (F(4))!) \\
 38395 &:= (((((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) + (F(-((3 - 9))))!) - (5)) \\
 38396 &:= (((((3!)! \times (-F(8))) / F(3!)) - F(9)) + (F(6))!) \\
 38398 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((-8!) - F(3!)) - F(9)) / (-F(8))) \\
 38399 &:= (((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) - (F(F(3)) + (9! / (-9)))) \\
 \\
 38400 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 00 \\
 38401 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 01 \\
 38402 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 02 \\
 38403 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 03 \\
 38404 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 04 \\
 38405 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 05 \\
 38406 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 06 \\
 38407 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 07 \\
 38408 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 08 \\
 38409 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 09 \\
 38410 &:= -F(3!)! / F(8) + F(F(4))! + 10
 \end{aligned}$$

- 38411 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 11$
- 38412 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 12$
- 38413 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 13$
- 38414 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 14$
- 38415 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 15$
- 38416 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 16$
- 38417 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 17$
- 38418 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 18$
- 38419 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 19$
- 38420 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 20$
- 38421 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 21$
- 38422 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 22$
- 38423 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 23$
- 38424 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 24$
- 38425 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 25$
- 38426 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 26$
- 38427 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 27$
- 38428 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 28$
- 38429 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 29$
- 38430 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 30$
- 38431 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 31$
- 38432 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 32$
- 38433 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 33$
- 38434 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 34$
- 38435 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 35$
- 38436 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 36$
- 38437 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 37$
- 38438 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 38$
- 38439 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 39$
- 38440 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 40$
- 38441 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 41$
- 38442 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 42$
- 38443 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 43$
- 38444 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 44$
- 38445 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 45$

- 38446 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 46$
- 38447 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 47$
- 38448 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 48$
- 38449 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 49$
- 38450 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 50$
- 38451 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 51$
- 38452 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 52$
- 38453 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 53$
- 38454 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 54$
- 38455 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 55$
- 38456 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 56$
- 38457 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 57$
- 38458 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 58$
- 38459 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 59$
- 38460 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 60$
- 38461 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 61$
- 38462 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 62$
- 38463 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 63$
- 38464 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 64$
- 38465 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 65$
- 38466 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 66$
- 38467 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 67$
- 38468 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 68$
- 38469 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 69$
- 38470 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 70$
- 38471 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 71$
- 38472 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 72$
- 38473 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 73$
- 38474 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 74$
- 38475 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 75$
- 38476 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 76$
- 38477 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 77$
- 38478 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 78$
- 38479 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 79$
- 38480 := $-F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4)!) + 80$

$$38481 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 81$$

$$38482 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 82$$

$$38483 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 83$$

$$38484 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 84$$

$$38485 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 85$$

$$38486 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 86$$

$$38487 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 87$$

$$38488 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 88$$

$$38489 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 89$$

$$38490 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 90$$

$$38491 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 91$$

$$38492 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 92$$

$$38493 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 93$$

$$38494 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 94$$

$$38495 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 95$$

$$38496 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 96$$

$$38497 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 97$$

$$38498 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 98$$

$$38499 := -F(3)!/F(8) + F(F(4))! + 99$$

$$38504 := ((F(3))! - ((F(F(8)) - (50))/(F(4))!))$$

$$38514 := ((F(F(3))) \times (-85 + 1)) + (F((F(4))!))!$$

$$38520 := (((F(3))! - ((F(8) \times 5!))) + (((2 + 0!)!))!$$

$$38523 := ((3 + 8!) - ((5!^2)/F(3)))$$

$$38524 := (((3!)! + (F(8))) \times 52) - F((F(4))!)$$

$$38526 := ((3! + 8!) - ((5!^2)/F(6)))$$

$$38527 := ((3!)! - ((-(8^5) + F(2)) - 7!))$$

$$38528 := (((F(3)^8) \times (-5 + 2)) + 8!)$$

$$38529 := -(((3!)! - (8! + ((5! - F(2)) \times (-9))))$$

$$38532 := (((3!)! + (F(8))) \times (53 - F(2)))$$

$$38533 := (((F(F(3))) \times (-85)) + (F(3))!) - F(3))$$

$$38534 := (((F(F(3))) \times (-85)) + (F(3))!) - F(F(F(4))))$$

$$38535 := ((F(3))! - (85 \times F((3 + 5))))$$

$$38536 := ((F(3) + (8^5)) - (F(3) \times (-6!)))$$

$$38537 := ((F(3))! - (((8!/5!) \times 3!) - F(F(7))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38538 &:= ((3 \times ((F(8) - 5!) \times 3!)) + 8!) \\ 38539 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(8) + (-53) \times F(9)))) \\ 38543 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times (-85)) + F((F(4)!)) + (F(3!))!) \\ 38544 &:= (((F(3)^8) \times 5!) + F(4!)) / F(F(4)) \\ 38547 &:= ((F(F(3)) + F(F(8))) + (5! \times (-F(4) + F(F(7)))) \\ 38555 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F((8 + 5)) + 5!) \times 5)) \\ 38556 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(8) \times (-5) + F((5 + 6)))) \\ 38557 &:= ((F(3) + 8!) + (-5) \times (5! + F(F(7)))) \\ 38568 &:= (F(3!) \times (F(8) - ((5! - 6!) \times 8))) \\ 38569 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((85 \times F(F(6))) - F(9))) \\ 38573 &:= (((-3) + 8!) + 5!) - (F(F(7)) \times F(3!)) \\ 38574 &:= (-(((F(3) - 8!) - 5!)) + (-F(F(7)) \times F((F(4)!))) \\ 38575 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((8!/5!) + F(7)) \times 5)) \\ 38576 &:= ((F(3!) \times ((-8) - 5!) + 7!) - (6!)) \\ 38577 &:= ((F(3!) + (8! - 5!)) - (7 \times F(F(7)))) \\ 38578 &:= -((((3! + 8) + 5!) \times F(7)) - 8!) \\ 38583 &:= (((3!)! \times 8) + ((-5) + F(F(8))) \times 3) \\ 38583 &:= (((3!)! \times 8) + ((-5) + F(F(8))) \times 3) \\ 38584 &:= (((3!)! + 8) \times (5 - (-8) \times (F(4)!))) \\ 38593 &:= ((-F(3)) \times F(F(8))) - (-5) - (9!/3!)) \\ 38594 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (((8 + 5!) \times 9) \times 4!)) \\ 38595 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((8!/5!) + 9) \times 5)) \\ 38597 &:= -((F(F(3)) - ((F((F(8) - 5))) \times F(9)) + (7!))) \\ 38598 &:= (((3!)! \times 8) + (F(-((5 - 9))) \times F(F(8)))) \\ 38599 &:= (((F(3) - (F(F(8)) \times (-5!))) / F(9)) - F(9)) \\ 38606 &:= ((3 \times F(F(8))) + ((6! + 0!) \times F(6))) \\ 38610 &:= (((3 - F(8)) + 6!) \times F(10)) \\ 38613 &:= (((F((F(3) \times 8)) - (F(6)!)) \times (-1)) - 3!!) \\ 38614 &:= (F(3) \times (((F(F(8)) \times 6) - 1) - F(4!))) \\ 38616 &:= (((3 + 8!) - 6!) - F(16)) \\ 38619 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(8) \times ((F(6) + 1) \times 9))) \\ 38624 &:= (-(((F(3) + (86))^2)) + F(4!)) \\ 38625 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(8) + (6!/(-2))) \times (-5))) \\ 38627 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((8!/((6 - 2)!)) + F(7))) \\ 38628 &:= (((3! \times F(8)) + 6!) \times (-2)) + 8! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38632 &:= -(((F(3!) - 8!) + ((F(6))!/((F(3) + 2)!))) \\ 38633 &:= ((F(3!)! - (F(F(8)) - ((F(F(6))^3 - F(3)))) \\ 38634 &:= (((F((3 \times 8))/(-6)) - 3!) + F(4!)) \\ 38635 &:= (((F((3 \times 8)) - (6))/3!) \times 5) \\ 38636 &:= ((F(F(3)) - F(F(8))) + ((F(F(6))^3 + (F(6))!)) \\ 38638 &:= (((3! + (8!/F(6)))/(-3)) + 8!) \\ 38639 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - 8!) + ((F(F(6)) \times (3!)!/9))) \\ \\ 38640 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 0 \\ 38641 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 1 \\ 38642 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 2 \\ 38643 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 3 \\ 38644 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 4 \\ 38645 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 5 \\ 38646 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 6 \\ 38647 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 7 \\ 38648 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 8 \\ 38649 &:= -F(3 \times 8)/6 + F(4!) + 9 \\ \\ 38654 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((-8!) - ((F(6))!/(-5!)))/(-4!)) \\ 38656 &:= ((F(3) \times ((8 - 6!) - 5!)) + (F(6))!) \\ 38657 &:= (F(F(3)) + (8! - ((F(6) + 5!) \times F(7)))) \\ 38666 &:= (((((3 + 8))!)/(6! + 6!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 38673 &:= (((((F(3!)!)/(-F(8))) + (F(F(6)) \times F(7))) + (F(3!)!)) \\ 38676 &:= (-((3! - ((F(8) \times (-6)) \times F(7)))) + (F(6))!) \\ 38677 &:= (-(((3! - 8!) + (6))) - (7 \times F(F(7)))) \\ 38678 &:= ((F(3) \times (F(8) + (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7)))) + 8!) \\ 38682 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((F(8) \times 6) \times F((8 - F(2))))) \\ 38687 &:= (-((F(3) - 8!)) - (F(-((F(6) - F(8)))) \times 7)) \\ 38689 &:= -(((F(((3 + 8) + 6)) - 8!) + F(9)) \\ 38696 &:= (F(3!) + (8! + ((F(6) \times F(9)) \times (-6)))) \\ 38697 &:= ((F(3!)! - (F(8) + (6 \times (F(9) + F(F(7)))))) \\ 38703 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(8)) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-0!)) \times F(3!))) \\ 38704 &:= (((3!)! \times (-F(8))) + ((F(F(7)) - 0!)^{F(F(4))}) \\ 38710 &:= (((3!)! + 8!) + (F(F(7)) \times (-10))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38715 &:= -(((F(3!) - 8!) + F((F(7) - ((1 - 5)))))) \\ 38717 &:= -((3! + ((-8) \times 7!) + F(17))) \\ 38722 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - 8!) + F((-7) + ((2 + 2)!))) \\ 38723 &:= -((F(((3 \times 8) - 7)) - (2^3)!)) \\ 38724 &:= ((F(F(3)) + 8!) - F(-((7 - 24))) \\ 38725 &:= ((F(3) + 8!) - F((7 + (2 \times 5)))) \\ 38726 &:= ((3 + 8!) - F((F(7) - ((2 - 6)))) \\ 38729 &:= ((3! + 8!) - F(((7 + F(2)) + 9)) \\ 38731 &:= ((F(3!) + 8!) - F((-7) + ((3 + 1)!)) \\ 38732 &:= ((F(3!)! - (F(F(8)) + ((-F(7)) \times (3!)! + 2))) \\ 38733 &:= (F((F(3) + F(8))) + (((7! - F(3)) \times F(3))) \\ 38734 &:= (F((F(3) + F(8))) + (((7! \times F(3)) - F(4))) \\ 38735 &:= (F(F(3)) + (8! - (F(7) \times (F(3) + 5!)))) \\ 38737 &:= (F((F(3) + F(8))) - ((7! \times (-3)) + 7!)) \\ 38738 &:= (((3 \times F(F(8))) - ((7! + 3!))) + F(F(8))) \\ 38739 &:= (((3 + 8!) + F(7)) - F((F(3!) + 9)) \\ 38742 &:= -((((F((-3) + F(8))) + (7!)) - F(4!)) + 2) \\ 38743 &:= (F((F(3) + F(8))) + (((7! + F(4)) \times F(3))) \\ 38744 &:= (((3 \times F(F(8))) - (7!)) + F(F((4 + 4))) \\ 38745 &:= ((F(3!)! - (-F(8)) \times ((F(7) + F(F(4))) \times (-5))) \\ 38746 &:= (((F(3) + 8!) - F((-7) + 4!)) + F(F(6))) \\ 38747 &:= (3 - ((F(F(8)) \times (-7) + F(4)) + (7!))) \\ 38748 &:= (((3 \times F(F(8))) - ((7! - (4)))) + F(F(8))) \\ 38749 &:= -((((F(3!) - 8!) + F((-7) + 4!)) - F(9)) \\ 38750 &:= ((3 + 8!) - (F(7) \times (5! + 0!))) \\ 38751 &:= -((F(3!) - ((8! - ((F(7) \times 5!) + 1)))) \\ 38752 &:= -(((3! - 8!) + ((F(7) \times 5!) + 2)) \\ 38753 &:= (-(((3! - 8!) + (F(7) \times 5!)) - F(F(3))) \\ 38754 &:= ((-3) + 8!) - ((F(7) \times 5!) + F(4)) \\ 38755 &:= (F(F(3)) \times (8! - ((F(7) \times 5!) + (5)))) \\ 38756 &:= ((F(3) + 8!) - ((F(7) \times 5!) + (6))) \\ 38757 &:= ((-3) + (8 \times 7!)) - (5! \times F(7)) \\ 38758 &:= ((3! + 8!) - ((F(7) \times 5!) + 8)) \\ 38759 &:= (F(3!) + (8! - ((F(7) \times 5!) + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$38760 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 0$$

$$38761 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 1$$

$$38762 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 2$$

$$38763 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 3$$

$$38764 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 4$$

$$38765 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 5$$

$$38766 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 6$$

$$38767 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 7$$

$$38768 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 8$$

$$38769 := -(-3 + 8)! \times F(7) + F(6)! + 9$$

$$38773 := -(((3!)! - ((8! + F(7)) - (7!/3!))))$$

$$38774 := -((((3!)! - F(F(8))) + (F(7) - (F(7)^4))))$$

$$38775 := (((F(3) + 8!) + F(7)) - (F(7) \times 5!))$$

$$38776 := -(((3!)! + ((8 \times (F(7) - 7!)) + 6!)))$$

$$38777 := ((-3) + 8!) + ((F(F(7)) - F(7)) \times (-7))$$

$$38778 := (F((3 + 8)) - ((7 \times F(F(7))) - 8!))$$

$$38779 := ((F(3!)! - (((8 - F(F(7))) \times (-7)) - F(9)))$$

$$38784 := (-3) \times (8! + (F(7) \times (-8^4)))$$

$$38787 := ((F(3!)! - ((F(8) - (7!/F(8))) \times (-7)))$$

$$38788 := ((3! \times (-F(8) - F(F(7)))) - (8 - 8!))$$

$$38794 := ((((-((3 - 8))! \times (-F(7))) + F(9)) + (F((F(4))!))!)$$

$$38796 := -((3! \times ((F(8) - 7) + (-9 \times 6!)))$$

$$38797 := -(((F(3) - 8!) + ((F(7) \times 9) \times F(7))))$$

$$38820 := ((F(F(3!)) + (8!/F(8))) \times 20)$$

$$38825 := ((F(F(3!)) + ((88^2))) \times 5)$$

$$38829 := (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(8) - (F((8 + 2)) \times F(9))))$$

$$38832 := (-((3! - 8!)) - ((F(8) + 3!!) \times 2))$$

$$38834 := (((3!)! - 8!)/8) + (F(F(F(3!))) \times 4)$$

$$38835 := ((3!)! + (8! - ((F(8)^{F(3)}) \times 5)))$$

$$38842 := ((-38) + 8!) + (((F(4))! \times (-2)))$$

$$38843 := (((3!)! + 8!) - (F((F(8)/F(4)))^3))$$

$$38844 := -((((3!)! - 8!) + ((F(8) \times (F(4))!) \times (F(4))!))$$

$$38846 := -((F((F(F(3)) + 8)) + (-8!) - (F(F(4)) \times (-6!))))$$

- 38848 := ((F(3!) × (8 - (8 × 4!))) + 8!)
- 38849 := ((-(((3!)! - F(F(8)))) + F((F(8) + F(F(4)))))) - F(9))
- 38854 := (-(((3!)! + ((F(8) - 8!) + (5)))) - ((F(4)!)!)
- 38859 := (-(((3!)! - (8! - F(8)))) - ((F(-(5 - 9)))!))
- 38860 := -(((3!)! + (((F(8) - 8!) + 6!) - 0!)))
- 38862 := (((3 + 8!) - F(8)) - (6! × 2))
- 38863 := -((F(F(3)) - (8! + ((-8) - 6!) × F(3))))
- 38864 := ((F(F(3)) × 8!) - ((8 + 6!) × F(F(4))))
- 38865 := -(((3!)! - ((F(8) × F((8 + 6))) × 5)))
- 38867 := -(((F((F(3) + 8)) - 8!) - (-6) × F(F(7))))
- 38869 := -(((F(3) - 8!) - (F(8) × (-69))))
- 38871 := (F(F(3!)) × (-F(8) - (-8) × (F(F(7)) + 1)))
- 38872 := (F(3!) × (-F(8) - (-8) × F((F(7) + 2))))
- 38873 := -(((F(F(3)) - 8!) + ((8 + F(F(7))) × 3!)))
- 38875 := ((F(3!)! - ((8! / (F(8) + (7))) + (5)))
- 38876 := ((F((F(3) + F(8))) + F(F(8))) + (-7) - 6!))
- 38877 := (3! - (-F(8)) × ((8 × F(F(7))) - F(7)))
- 38878 := -((F(3) + ((8! / (F(8) + (7))) - 8!))
- 38883 := ((F((F(3) + F(8))) + F(F(8))) - ((8 - F(3)))!)
- 38885 := -((F(F(3!)) - (F(F(8)) + (F((-8) + F(8))) × 5!)))
- 38886 := ((F((F(F(3)) + 8)) × (-F(8))) + (8! - 6!))
- 38887 := (((3!)! + (8! - (8! / F(8)))) - F(F(7)))
- 38889 := ((-3) + 8!) - ((F(8) + F(8)) × F(9))
- 38891 := ((F(3!)! - (((F(8) + F(8)) × F(9)) + 1))
- 38892 := (F(F(3)) × (8! + ((F(8) × F(9)) × (-2))))
- 38893 := (F(F(3)) + (8! - ((F(8) × F(9)) × F(3))))
- 38894 := ((F(3) + 8!) - ((F(8) × F(9)) × F(F(4))))
- 38896 := ((F(3) × (-8 × 89)) + (F(6)!)
- 38898 := (3! - (((F(8) + F(8)) × F(9)) - 8!))
- 38904 := (((3!)! × ((F(8) + F(9)) - 0!)) + (4!))
- 38906 := (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(-(F(8) - F(9)))) × (-((0! - (6))))!))
- 38913 := -((((3!)! - (((8! + F(9)) - 1))) + 3!))
- 38914 := (-(((3!)! - (8! + F(9)))) - ((F((1 × 4)))!))
- 38916 := ((F(3!)! - ((F(-(F(8) - F(9)))) + 1) × 6))
- 38920 := -(((3!)! - ((8! - (F(9) × 20))))

- 38922** := $((F(3!))! - (F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) \times (F((2 + 2))))!))$
- 38923** := $((F(F(3)) + 8!) + (F(F((9 - 2))) \times (-3!)))$
- 38924** := $((F(3) + 8!) - (F(F((9 - 2))) \times (F(4))!))$
- 38927** := $((((3!)! - 8) \times F((9 + F(2)))) - F(F(7)))$
- 38932** := $((F(3!))! - (((-8) + F(9)) - 3!) \times (-2)))$
- 38933** := $-((F((3! + 8)) - ((F(9)^3) + 3!)))$
- 38934** := $((((3!)! \times 8) + (9^3)) \times (F(4))!)$
- 38936** := $(F(3!) - ((-8) - (9 \times (3!)!)) \times 6)$
- 38937** := $((3! + 8!) - (F(9)^{F(3)})) - F(F(7))$
- 38939** := $((F(3!))! - (F(8) + ((F(9) + 3!) \times F(9))))$
- 38942** := $(-((3! - 8!)) - ((-F(9)) + ((F(4))!)! \times 2))$
- 38943** := $((3 \times F(8)) - ((-9) \times (F(4))!) \times (3!)!)$
- 38944** := $((F(3) \times F(F(8))) + ((9! + F(4!))/4!))$
- 38945** := $((F(3!))! - (((8 \times F(9)) + F(4)) \times 5))$
- 38946** := $((-3!) \times F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) - (-4!) - (F(6))!)$
- 38947** := $(-F(3!) + (-F(8)) \times (9 + (F((F(4))!) \times (-F(F(7))))))$
- 38948** := $((F((3! + 8)) - F(9)) \times (-4)) + 8!$
- 38952** := $((F(3!))! - (8 \times ((F(9) \times 5) + F(2))))$
- 38953** := $((F(3!))! - ((F(8) + (F(9) \times 5!))/3))$
- 38954** := $-(((3! - 8!) + ((F(9) \times 5!)/F(4))))$
- 38956** := $-((((3!)! - ((8! - F(9)))) + F((5!/F(6))))))$
- 38957** := $(-3) + (8 \times ((F(9) \times (-5)) + 7!))$
- 38958** := $-((F(3) + (((8 \times F(9)) \times 5) - 8!)))$
- 38960** := $((F(3!))! - ((8 \times F(9)) \times (6 - 0!)))$
- 38963** := $((F(3!))! - (F((8 + 9)) - (6!/3)))$
- 38964** := $((3! + 8) - (-9 \times 6!)) \times (F(4))!$
- 38968** := $-((F(3!) + ((8!/(9 + F(F(6)))) - 8!)))$
- 38973** := $((-3) + 8!) + ((-9) + F(F(7))) \times (-3!))$
- 38974** := $(-((F(3) - 8!)) + ((9 - F(F(7))) \times (F(4))!))$
- 38975** := $-((F(F(3)) + ((8! - (9! \times F(7)))/5!)))$
- 38976** := $-((3! \times ((8! - (9! \times F(7)))/6!)))$
- 38984** := $((F(3!))! - (8!/(9 + F(8)))) + F((F(4))!)$
- 38994** := $((F(3!))! + (((F(8) - F(9)) \times F(9)) \times F(4)))$
- 38995** := $(F(F(3)) + (8! - (F(9) \times (F(9) + (5))))))$
- 38996** := $((F(3!) \times (-F(8))) - (F(9) \times F(9))) + (F(6))!$

- 38997** := $((F(3!))! - (F(8) \times (-9) + (9!/7!)))$
38998 := $(-(F(3)) + (((F(8) - 9)! / (-9!)) + 8!))$
38999 := $((F(3!))! - (((F(8) - 9)! + 9!) / 9!))$
39024 := $((F(3!))! - ((9 - 0!) - 2)^4)$
39026 := $((39 \times ((0! + 2)!))! + F(F(F(6))))$
39028 := $((F((F(3) \times 9)) / (0 - 2)) + 8!)$
39033 := $((F(3!))! - (9 \times (-0!) + F((F(3) \times 3!))))$
39034 := $((F(3!))! - ((-9) - 0!) + (3!^4))$
39036 := $(-(3!) \times (F((9 + 0!)) - (3^{F(6)})))$
39042 := $((3! \times 9) \times (0! + ((F(4))!)) + 2)$
39045 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (-F((9 + 0!)))) + (F((F(4))!))! - 5!)$
39054 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) + (-((9 + 0!)^5)) / F(F(4))))$
39060 := $((F(3!))! - (F((9 - 0!)) \times 60))$
39062 := $((F(3!))! - (F(9) \times (0! + (6^2))))$
39073 := $((3! + F(9)) + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) + 3!)$
39074 := $((F((F(3) + 9)) \times (-0! + F(7))) + (F((F(4))!))!)$
39084 := $((3! \times 9) + F((0! + 8))) \times (F(4))!$
39094 := $-((3! \times (F(9) + 0!)) - (F(9)^{F(4)}))$
39095 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9) + 0!)^{F(F(9-5))}))$
39096 := $((3!)! \times F((9 + 0!)) - (9!/6!))$
39102 := $((3!)! - F(9)) \times (F(10) + 2)$
39103 := $((3!)! - 9) \times F(10) - F(3)$
39104 := $((3!)! - 9) \times F(10) - F(F(F(4)))$
39105 := $((3!)! - 9) \times F((1 + 0!) \times 5)$
39123 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (-F((9 + 1)) + 2)) + (F(3!))!)$
39129 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9) + 1)^2) - F(9))$
39130 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9) + 1) \times F((F(3!) + 0!))))$
39132 := $((F(3!))! - (9 \times 132))$
39137 := $((F(3!))! - (91^{F(3)} / 7))$
39143 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9)^{-1+F(4)})) - F(F(3!)))$
39144 := $((3!)! \times (-9 + 1)) + F(4!) - (4!)$
39147 := $(3 + ((F((9 - 1)) \times F((F(4))!)) \times F(F(7))))$
39155 := $((F(3!))! - (F((9 - 1) + 5)) \times 5)$
39156 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9))^{F(F(-1+5))}) + F(6))$

$$\begin{aligned} 39157 &:= ((F(3) + ((9 - 1)!) - (5 \times F(F(7)))) \\ 39158 &:= (-(3!) - ((F(9)^{F(-1+5)}) - 8!)) \\ 39159 &:= ((F(3)!)! - ((9 + ((1 \times 5)!) \times 9)) \\ 39162 &:= ((F(3)!)! - ((F(9) \times F((1 + F(6)))) + 2)) \\ 39163 &:= (3 + (F((9 + 1)) \times (6! - F(3)))) \\ 39164 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (F(9)^{1 \times 6 - 4})) \\ 39165 &:= ((F(F(3)) \times (-F((9 + 1)))) + (F((6!/5)!))!) \\ 39166 &:= (3! - (F((9 + 1)) \times (F(6) - 6!))) \\ 39167 &:= (((3! \times 9) \times (1 + 6!)) + F(F(7))) \\ 39168 &:= (((F((3 + 9)) \times (-1)) \times F(6)) + 8!) \\ 39174 &:= (((F(3!) \times F(9)) \times F((-1 + F(7)))) + (F(4)!) \\ 39176 &:= -((((F((3 + 9)) - 1) - 7!) \times F(6))) \\ 39178 &:= ((F(F(3)) \times (-F((9 + 1)))) + ((F(7) + 8!))) \\ 39183 &:= -((F(F(3)!) - ((9 \times (1 + F(8)))^{F(3)}))) \\ 39184 &:= (F(3!) \times (((9 - 1)!) + F(F(8)) - F(4!))) \\ 39186 &:= (((3! \times (-9)) \times F((1 \times 8))) + (F(6)!) \\ 39196 &:= (-((F(3) + ((F(9) - 1) \times F(9)))) + (F(6)!) \\ 39198 &:= (((F(3) - F(9)) - 1) \times F(9)) + 8! \\ 39199 &:= ((F(3)!)! + (((F(9) + 1) - (F(9) \times F(9)))) \\ 39204 &:= ((3! \times (F(9) - F(2)))^{F(F(04))}) \\ 39205 &:= (F(F(3)!) + (((F(9)^{2+0!}) - 5!)) \\ 39208 &:= (((3!)! + F((9 \times 2) + 0!)) \times 8) \\ 39219 &:= ((F(3)!)! - ((F(9)^2) - F((1 + 9)))) \\ 39220 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (F((9 + F(2))) \times 20)) \\ 39223 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (F(((9 - 2) \times 2)) + 3!)) \\ 39228 &:= (-(3) - (((F(9) - F(2))^2) - 8!)) \\ 39230 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (((F(9) - F(2))^{F(3)} + 0!)) \\ 39231 &:= ((F(3)!)! - ((F(9) - F(2))^{3-1})) \\ 39232 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (F(9) \times (2^{3+2}))) \\ 39233 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (((F(9) - F(2))^{F(3)} - F(3))) \\ 39234 &:= ((F(3)!)! - (((F(9) - F(2))^{F(3)} - F(4))) \\ 39235 &:= ((F(3)!)! - ((9 \times ((2 + 3)!) + (5))) \\ 39238 &:= -((F(3) + ((9 \times ((2 + 3)!) - 8!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$39240 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 0$$

$$39241 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 1$$

$$39242 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 2$$

$$39243 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 3$$

$$39244 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 4$$

$$39245 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 5$$

$$39246 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 6$$

$$39247 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 7$$

$$39248 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 8$$

$$39249 := F(3!)! - 9 \times (2 + F(4))! + 9$$

$$39250 := ((F(3!)! - ((-9) \times (F(2) - 5!)) - 0!))$$

$$39253 := ((F(3!)! - ((F(9)^2) - F((5 + 3!))))$$

$$39254 := ((F(3!)! - ((9 \times (-2) + 5!) + (4)))$$

$$39256 := (-((F(3) - (9 \times (2 - 5!)))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$39257 := ((F(F(3!)) \times (F(9) \times F((2 \times 5)))) - F(7))$$

$$39258 := (F(F(3)) \times ((9 \times (2 - 5!)) + 8!))$$

$$39262 := ((F(3!)! - (F(9) + (2^{F(6)+2})))$$

$$39264 := (((((3!)! \times 9) + ((2^6))) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$39265 := (((F(3!)! + (F(9) \times (-2))) - F((F(F(6)) - (5))))$$

$$39266 := (((3 - F(9)) \times F((F(2) + F(6)))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$39267 := ((F(3!)! - ((9^2) \times (6 + 7)))$$

$$39270 := (F(F(3!)) \times (F(9) \times F(((2 + 7) + 0!))))$$

$$39274 := -((F(F(3!)) - (-9) + (F((2 + 7))^{F(4)})))$$

$$39278 := -((((3!)! + (F((9 + 2)))) + F(F(7))) - 8!))$$

$$39280 := ((F(3!)! - (F((9 - 2)) \times 80))$$

$$39288 := (((((F(3)^9) \times (-2)) + 8!) - 8)$$

$$39291 := (F(F(3!)) \times ((F(9) \times F((F(2) + 9))) + 1))$$

$$39295 := ((F(3!)! + ((F((9 + F(2))) - (9 \times 5!))))$$

$$39297 := (3! + (((F(9)^2) \times F(9)) - F(7)))$$

$$39299 := ((F(3!)! - (F(((9 - 2) + 9)) + F(9)))$$

$$39300 := (-3) + ((F(9)^3) - (00!))$$

$$39302 := (-3) + ((F(9)^3) + ((0 \times 2)!))$$

$$39305 := (F(3) + ((F(9)^3) - ((0 \times 5)!))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39307 &:= (F(3) + ((F(9)^3) + ((0 \times 7)!)) \\ 39308 &:= (3 + ((F(9)^3) + ((0 \times 8)!)) \\ 39309 &:= (-3) + (((F(9)^3) - 0!) + 9) \\ \\ 39310 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 0 \\ 39311 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 1 \\ 39312 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 2 \\ 39313 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 3 \\ 39314 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 4 \\ 39315 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 5 \\ 39316 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 6 \\ 39317 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 7 \\ 39318 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 8 \\ 39319 &:= 3! + F(9)^3 \times 1 + 9 \\ \\ 39320 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 + F(F(3)))^{2+0!})) \\ 39322 &:= -((3! - ((F(9)^3) + ((2 + 2)!))) \\ 39324 &:= (-3) + (((F(9)^3) - F(2)) + 4!) \\ 39325 &:= (F(3!) + ((F(9)^3) + F((2 + 5)))) \\ 39326 &:= ((3! + (F(9)^3)) + (2 \times F(6))) \\ 39328 &:= (((-3) + F(9)) \times (-32)) + 8! \\ 39329 &:= -((F(3!) - (((F(9)^3) - F(2)) + F(9)))) \\ 39330 &:= ((F(3) + (F(9)^3)) + ((3 + 0)!)) \\ 39331 &:= (3 + ((F(9)^3) + ((3 + 1)!)) \\ 39334 &:= (3 + (((F(9)^3) + 3) + 4!)) \\ 39335 &:= (F(F(3)) + ((F(9)^3) - (3! \times (-5)))) \\ 39337 &:= -(((3! - (F(9)^3)) - (3 \times F(7)))) \\ 39338 &:= ((3! - F(9)) + (3! \times (3^8))) \\ 39340 &:= ((F(3) + (F(9)^3)) + F((F((F(4))!) + 0!)) \\ 39341 &:= (((3^9) \times F(3)) - 4!) - 1 \\ 39344 &:= ((3! + F(9)) + (34^{F(4)})) \\ 39346 &:= ((F(3!) + ((F(9)^3))) + F((F(4) + (6)))) \\ 39347 &:= (3! + (((F(9)^3) + 4!) + F(7))) \\ 39349 &:= (F(3!) + (((F(9)^3) + F(4)) + F(9))) \\ 39350 &:= ((F(3!))! - (9 + ((F(3!) \times 5!) + 0!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39351 &:= ((F(3!))! - (9 + (F(3!) \times ((5 \times 1)!))) \\
 39353 &:= (-((3! - (F(9)^3))) + F((5 \times F(3)))) \\
 39354 &:= ((-((3^9)) + 3!) \times (-5) + F(4)) \\
 39355 &:= ((F(3!) \times (((9 - F(3)))! - 5!)) - (5)) \\
 39357 &:= (-3) - (F((9 - 3)) \times (5! - 7!)) \\
 39359 &:= (F(F(3!)) + ((F(9)^{-F(3)+5}) + F(9))) \\
 39373 &:= (((3^9) \times F(3)) + F(7)) - 3! \\
 39375 &:= ((3! + (F(9)^3)) + (F(7) \times 5)) \\
 39376 &:= -(((3! - (F(9)^3)) + (F(7) \times (-6)))) \\
 39378 &:= -(((3! \times (F(9 + 3)) + F(7))) - 8!) \\
 39379 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-((F(9)^{F(3)})) - (F(F(7)) \times (-9)))) \\
 39381 &:= ((F(3!))! - (938 + 1)) \\
 39383 &:= (F(3!) + (9 + ((3^8) \times 3!))) \\
 39385 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 + F(3)) \times 85)) \\
 39386 &:= ((-(((3 + 9)!)/(F(3)!)) + (F(F(8)) + (F(6)!))) \\
 39389 &:= (((3!)! + F((F(9)/F(3)))) \times (8 + 9)) \\
 39390 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-93) \times (-9 - 0!)) \\
 39392 &:= (F(3!) + ((9 + (3^9)) \times 2)) \\
 39403 &:= -(((F(F(3!)) - ((F(9)^{F(4)})) - (-((0! - 3!)))) \\
 39404 &:= ((F(3!))! - (940 - 4!)) \\
 39406 &:= ((3 + (F(9)^{F(4)})) \times F((0! + F(6)))) \\
 39407 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - 0!)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 39414 &:= ((-((3^9)) - 4!) \times (1 - F(4))) \\
 39415 &:= -((F(3!) - (((F(9)^{F(4)} - 1) + 5!))) \\
 39416 &:= -(((F(3!) - ((F(9)^{F(4)})) - (-((1 - 6)!))) \\
 39417 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 + ((4 + 1)!)) \times 7)) \\
 \\
 39420 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 0 \\
 39421 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 1 \\
 39422 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 2 \\
 39423 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 3 \\
 39424 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 4 \\
 39425 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 5 \\
 39426 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39427 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 7 \\ 39428 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 8 \\ 39429 &:= F(3!)! - (F(9) - 4)^2 + 9 \\ 39430 &:= ((3! + (F(9)^{F(4)})) + ((3! - 0!))!) \\ 39431 &:= ((((-3) - F(9)) \times 4!) + (F(3!))!) - 1 \\ 39432 &:= (F(3!) + ((F(9)^{F(4)} + ((3 + 2))!)) \\ 39433 &:= (-F(3)) + (F((F(9) - 4!)) \times ((3!)! - 3)) \\ 39434 &:= (F(3) \times (F(9) + ((4! + 3)^{F(4)})) \\ 39435 &:= (F(3!) + (((F(9)^{F(4)} + 3) + 5!)) \\ 39436 &:= (-(((F(3) \times F(9)) \times F((4 + 3)))) + (F(6))!) \\ 39437 &:= (((3! \times (9 + 4!))^{F(3)} + F(F(7))) \\ 39438 &:= ((((-3) - F(9)) \times 4!) + 3!) + 8! \\ 39440 &:= ((3! + F(9)) \times (F((4 \times 4) - 0!)) \\ 39442 &:= (-((3! - (F(9)^{F(4)}))) + F((4!/2))) \\ 39443 &:= (F(3!) + (F((F(9) - 4!)) \times (-F(4) + 3!))) \\ 39444 &:= (3! \times ((9^4) + F((F(4) + (4)))))) \\ 39445 &:= (-3) + (((F(9)^{F(4)} + 4!) + 5!)) \\ 39446 &:= -(((F(3) - (F(9)^{F(4)})) - (4! \times 6))) \\ 39447 &:= (((3!)! \times (-9)) + ((F(4)^{F(F(4)!)} \times 7)) \\ 39448 &:= (((F(3) - (-9) \times 4!)) \times (-4) + 8! \\ 39452 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times 4!) + (52))) \\ 39453 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((-9) \times (4! - 5!) + 3)) \\ 39454 &:= (3! + (((F(9)^{F(4)} + 5!) + 4!)) \\ 39456 &:= (3! \times ((9^4) + (5!/F(6)))) \\ 39457 &:= ((F(3!))! - (9 + ((F(F(4)) + 5!) \times 7))) \\ 39458 &:= (F(3) + ((9 \times (4! - 5!)) + 8!)) \\ 39459 &:= (F(F(3)) + (((F(9)^{F(4)} + 5!) + F(9))) \\ 39462 &:= (3! \times ((9^4) + (F(6) \times 2))) \\ 39463 &:= -((((F(F(3)) + (F(9) \times 4)) - (F(6))!) + 3!)) \\ 39464 &:= -((F((F(3) \times 9)) - (((F(4))! \times (-6!)) + F(4!)))) \\ 39465 &:= ((-((3! + (9^{F(4)}))) + (F(6))!) - 5!) \\ 39466 &:= (((((3!)! - 9!) + F(4!))/(-F(6))) - F(6)) \\ 39467 &:= (((((3!)! - 9!) + F(4!))/(-F(6))) - 7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39468 &:= ((3! \times ((F(9) \times (-4)) - (6))) + 8!) \\ 39469 &:= -((((F(F(3)) + ((F(9) \times 4!))) - (F(6))!) + F(9))) \\ 39470 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(9) \times (4! + ((7 \times 0)!))) \\ 39474 &:= ((F(3) + (F(9)^{F(4)})) + (7 \times 4!)) \\ 39475 &:= (((3! + F(9)) \times F((F(4) + F(7)))) - (5)) \\ 39476 &:= -((((F(F(3)) + F((-9) + 4!))) + F(F(7))) - (F(6))!) \\ 39477 &:= (((F(3!))! - F((9 + (-((4 - 7)!))) - F(F(7))) \\ 39478 &:= -((F(3) - (((9 - 4)! \times (-7)) + 8!)) \\ 39479 &:= -((F(F(3)) - ((F(9) + (F(4))!) \times F((7 + 9)))) \\ \\ 39480 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 0 \\ 39481 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 1 \\ 39482 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 2 \\ 39483 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 3 \\ 39484 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 4 \\ 39485 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 5 \\ 39486 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 6 \\ 39487 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 7 \\ 39488 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 8 \\ 39489 &:= (3! + F(9)) \times F(4! - 8) + 9 \\ \\ 39490 &:= (((3!)! - F((9/F(4)))) \times F((9 + 0!))) \\ 39492 &:= (3! \times ((9^4) + F((9 - F(2)))) \\ 39493 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) \times 4!) + 9) + F(3))) \\ 39493 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) \times 4!) + 9) + F(3))) \\ 39494 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) \times 4!) + F(9)) - 4!)) \\ 39496 &:= ((F(F(3)) - ((F(9) \times 4!) + 9)) + (F(6))!) \\ 39497 &:= (-((3! - ((F(9)^{F(4)} - F(9)))) + F(F(7))) \\ 39498 &:= (3 - (((F(9) \times 4!) + 9) - 8!)) \\ 39499 &:= (((3! + (F(9)^{F(F(4))}) \times F(9)) - 9) \\ 39502 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times ((5 - 0)!)) + 2)) \\ 39503 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times ((5 - 0)!)) + F(F(3)))) \\ 39504 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(9) \times (((5 \times 0) + 4)!)) \\ 39505 &:= ((F(3!))! + (-95 - ((0! + (5)!))) \\ 39506 &:= (F(3) + ((-F(9)) \times ((5 - 0)!)) + (F(6))!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 39507** := $((F(3!))! + ((F(9) + ((5! + 0!) \times (-7))))$
39511 := $((((F(3!))! - ((F((9 - 5)))!)) - (F(11)))$
39513 := $((F(3!))! - (-(((F(9) - 5!) - 1)) + 3!))$
39514 := $((F(3!))! - (-F(9)) + (5! \times (1 + (F(4)!))))$
39517 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times ((5 - 1))!) - F(7)))$
39519 := $((F(3!))! - (9 \times F((F(F((5 - 1))) + 9))))$
39523 := $((F(3!))! - (((F(9) + 5!)/2) + 3!))$
39524 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - F(F((5 + 2)))) \times (-4)))$
39527 := $((F(3!))! - ((9 + 52) \times F(7)))$
39532 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - (5! \times (-3))) \times 2))$
39533 := $(((((F(3!) \times (-9)) + (5)) + (F(3!))!) - ((3!))!))$
39534 := $((F(3) + 9) \times ((5 \times (3!))! - (F(4)!))$
39535 := $((F(3!))! - (((F(9) + 5!) + 3) \times 5))$
39536 := $(-(((F(3) \times (9 + 5))^{F(3)})) + (F(6))!)$
39538 := $((3! \times (-9 - 5!)) - F(3!)) + 8!$
39539 := $((F(3!))! - ((95 + 3!!) - F(9)))$
39540 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - (F(9) \times ((-5!) - ((F(4)!))! - 0!)))$
39543 := $(-(3!) - ((-(9! - 5!)) + F(4!))/F(3!))$
39544 := $((F(3!))! - (((F(9) \times 5) + 4!) \times 4))$
39545 := $((3! - F(F(F((9 - 5)))))) \times F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))$
39546 := $(3! \times (-9) + (5! \times F((4 + 6))))$
39547 := $((F(3!))! - (((9 \times 5!)/F(F(4))) + F(F(7))))$
39548 := $((((F(3!) - (9! - 5!)) + F(4!))/(-8))$
39549 := $((-3!) - ((F(9) - (5))) \times F(4!))/F(9))$

39550 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 0$
39551 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 1$
39552 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 2$
39553 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 3$
39554 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 4$
39555 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 5$
39556 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 6$
39557 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 7$
39558 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 8$
39559 := $F(3!)! - (F(9) + 5!) \times 5 + 9$

$$39560 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 0$$

$$39561 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 1$$

$$39562 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 2$$

$$39563 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 3$$

$$39564 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 4$$

$$39565 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 5$$

$$39566 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 6$$

$$39567 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 7$$

$$39568 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 8$$

$$39569 := -F(3!) \times 95 + F(6)! + 9$$

$$39570 := (- (3!) + (F(9) \times ((5 \times F(F(7))) - 0!)))$$

$$39571 := -(((3!)! + ((F(9) - 5) - ((7 + 1)!)))$$

$$39572 := ((F(3!)! - (F(9) \times (F((-5) + F(7)) + F(2))))$$

$$39573 := ((-((3 \times 9)) + ((-5) + F(7))!) - 3!)$$

$$39574 := ((F(3!)! - (-F(9) + ((5! \times F(7))/F(F(4))))))$$

$$39575 := ((F(3!)! - (-95) + (7 \times 5!))$$

$$39576 := (((F(3) - 95) + 7!) \times F(6))$$

$$39578 := -(((3!)! - (((F(9) + 5!)/(-7) + 8!)))$$

$$39580 := (((F(3!)! - ((F((9 - 5)))!)) - (F(8) - 0!))$$

$$39582 := ((F(3!)! - ((F((9 + 5)) - 8) \times 2))$$

$$39584 := ((F(3!) \times (-95)) + ((8! + 4!))$$

$$39586 := (F(F(3)) \times ((-((9 + 5)) + 8!) - 6!))$$

$$39587 := (((F((3 + 9)) \times (-5)) + 8!) - F(7))$$

$$39589 := -(((3!)! - (((9! - 5!) + F(8))/9))$$

$$39590 := -(((F((3! + 9)) + 5!) - ((9 - 0!)!))$$

$$39591 := -(((3^{F(9-5)!}) - ((9 - 1)!))$$

$$39592 := ((F(3!)! - (9^{F(-5+9)}) - F(2)))$$

$$39595 := ((F(3!)! - (((F(9) + 5!) - 9) \times 5))$$

$$39596 := -(((((-((3 - 9)))! - ((5 - 9))) - (F(6)!))$$

$$39597 := (F(F(3!)) + (-F(9) + ((5 \times F(9)) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$39598 := ((F(3!) \times (F(9) - 5!)) - (F(9) - 8!))$$

$$39599 := (((F(3!)! - ((F((9 - 5)))!)) - (9/9))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39600 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 00 \\ 39601 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 01 \\ 39602 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 02 \\ 39603 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 03 \\ 39604 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 04 \\ 39605 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 05 \\ 39606 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 06 \\ 39607 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 07 \\ 39608 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 08 \\ 39609 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 09 \\ 39610 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 10 \\ 39611 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 11 \\ 39612 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 12 \\ 39613 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 13 \\ 39614 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 14 \\ 39615 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 15 \\ 39616 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 16 \\ 39617 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 17 \\ 39618 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 18 \\ 39619 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 19 \\ 39620 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 20 \\ 39621 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 21 \\ 39622 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 22 \\ 39623 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 23 \\ 39624 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 24 \\ 39625 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 25 \\ 39626 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 26 \\ 39627 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 27 \\ 39628 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 28 \\ 39629 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 29 \\ 39630 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 30 \\ 39631 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 31 \\ 39632 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 32 \\ 39633 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 33 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39634 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 34 \\ 39635 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 35 \\ 39636 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 36 \\ 39637 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 37 \\ 39638 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 38 \\ 39639 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 39 \\ 39640 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 40 \\ 39641 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 41 \\ 39642 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 42 \\ 39643 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 43 \\ 39644 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 44 \\ 39645 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 45 \\ 39646 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 46 \\ 39647 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 47 \\ 39648 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 48 \\ 39649 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 49 \\ 39650 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 50 \\ 39651 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 51 \\ 39652 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 52 \\ 39653 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 53 \\ 39654 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 54 \\ 39655 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 55 \\ 39656 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 56 \\ 39657 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 57 \\ 39658 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 58 \\ 39659 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 59 \\ 39660 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 60 \\ 39661 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 61 \\ 39662 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 62 \\ 39663 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 63 \\ 39664 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 64 \\ 39665 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 65 \\ 39666 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 66 \\ 39667 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 67 \\ 39668 &:= -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 68 \end{aligned}$$

$$39669 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 69$$

$$39670 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 70$$

$$39671 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 71$$

$$39672 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 72$$

$$39673 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 73$$

$$39674 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 74$$

$$39675 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 75$$

$$39676 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 76$$

$$39677 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 77$$

$$39678 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 78$$

$$39679 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 79$$

$$39680 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 80$$

$$39681 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 81$$

$$39682 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 82$$

$$39683 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 83$$

$$39684 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 84$$

$$39685 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 85$$

$$39686 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 86$$

$$39687 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 87$$

$$39688 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 88$$

$$39689 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 89$$

$$39690 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 90$$

$$39691 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 91$$

$$39692 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 92$$

$$39693 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 93$$

$$39694 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 94$$

$$39695 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 95$$

$$39696 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 96$$

$$39697 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 97$$

$$39698 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 98$$

$$39699 := -(-3 + 9)! + F(6)! + 99$$

$$39701 := ((F(3!))! - (9 + F(((F(7) + 0!) + 1))))$$

$$39703 := (-((F((3! + 9)) + 7)) + (F((03)!)))!$$

$$39704 := -(((F((3! + 9)) - ((7 + 0!)!) + (F(4)!)))!$$

$$39705 := -(((F((3! + 9)) - ((7 + 0!)!) + (5)))$$

$$39708 := (((-3) \times F(9)) \times (7 - 0!)) + 8!$$

$$39710 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 0$$

$$39711 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 1$$

$$39712 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 2$$

$$39713 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 3$$

$$39714 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 4$$

$$39715 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 5$$

$$39716 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 6$$

$$39717 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 7$$

$$39718 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 8$$

$$39719 := -F(3! + 9) + (7 + 1)! + 9$$

$$39720 := ((F(3!))! - ((-9) + F((F(7) + 2))) - 0!))$$

$$39723 := ((3 \times (F(9) - F(F(7)))) + (2^3)!))$$

$$39724 := ((F(3!))! + ((F(9) - (7!/(2 \times 4))))))$$

$$39725 := ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) \times (-7))/(-2)) \times 5))$$

$$39727 := ((F(3!))! - (((F((-9) + F(7))))!)/2 + F(F(7))))$$

$$39728 := (((F(3!) \times (-9)) + (7! - 2)) \times 8)$$

$$39731 := -((F((F(3!) + 9)) - (-7!) + F(((3 + 1)!))))$$

$$39732 := (3! + (9 \times (F(F(7)) + F((F(F(3!)) - 2))))))$$

$$39733 := -(((3!)! - ((F(9) - F((F(7) \times F(3)))))/(-3))))$$

$$39734 := -((F((3! + 9)) + ((-7!) \times F(3!)) - (4!))))$$

$$39735 := ((F(3!))! - (9 \times ((7 + 3!) \times 5)))$$

$$39736 := (F(3!) \times ((-9) + 7!) - (F(3)^6))$$

$$39737 := ((((-3) \times F(9)) + 7!) \times F(3!)) + F(F(7)))$$

$$39738 := ((F(3) \times (-97 \times 3)) + 8!)$$

$$39739 := -((F(F(3!)) - ((-9!) + ((F(7) - 3!)!)/(-9))))$$

$$39741 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times (-7) + 4!) + 1))$$

$$39742 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(9))^{F(7-4)}/2))$$

$$39743 := ((F(3!))! - (F((9 - 7)) + (4!^{F(3)})))$$

$$39745 := ((-3) + ((-F(9)) \times F(F(7)) - (4!))) \times (-5))$$

$$39746 := (((3!)! - ((F(9) - (7!/(-4)))))) + (F(6)!))$$

$$39747 := -(((3!)! - ((F(9) + (7)) \times F((F(4) + F(7))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39748 &:= (((F(3) + 9) \times F(7)) \times (-4)) + 8!) \\
 39753 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - (7)) \times F((5 + 3)))) \\
 39755 &:= ((F(-((3 - 9))))! - ((7 - 5!) \times (-5))) \\
 39756 &:= (-((F(3) + ((F(9) \times F(7)) + 5!))) + (F(6))!) \\
 39758 &:= (F(F(3)) \times (-(((F(9) \times F(7)) + 5!) - 8!))) \\
 39760 &:= (F(F(3)) \times ((9! - 7!)/(F(6) + 0!))) \\
 39761 &:= (F(F(3)) + (((9! - 7!)/(F(6) + 1)))) \\
 39762 &:= (F(3) + ((9! - 7!)/(F(6) + F(2)))) \\
 39764 &:= (((((3!)/9) \times (-7)) + (F(6))!) + 4) \\
 39765 &:= (((((3!)/9) \times (-7)) + (F(6))!) + (5)) \\
 39766 &:= (((((3!)/9) \times (-7)) + (F(6))!) + 6) \\
 39767 &:= (((((3!)/9) \times (-7)) + (F(6))!) + 7) \\
 39768 &:= (((3 - (9!/7!)) \times F(6)) + 8!) \\
 39769 &:= (((((3!)/9) \times (-7)) + (F(6))!) + 9) \\
 39772 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) + (7)) + F(F(7))) \times 2)) \\
 39773 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-((9 \times 7) + F((F(7) + F(3))))) \\
 39774 &:= ((3! + (9 \times 7!)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-4!))) \\
 39776 &:= -((((F(3) \times (F(9) - 7!)) + 7!) \times F(6))) \\
 39777 &:= ((F(3!) \times (-97 + 7!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 39778 &:= -(((3!))! - (9 + ((F(7) \times F(7)) + 8!))) \\
 \\
 39780 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 0 \\
 39781 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 1 \\
 39782 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 2 \\
 39783 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 3 \\
 39784 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 4 \\
 39785 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 5 \\
 39786 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 6 \\
 39787 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 7 \\
 39788 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 8 \\
 39789 &:= 3!! \times F(9) \times F(7)/8 + 9 \\
 \\
 39792 &:= (F(3!) \times (-(((F(9) - 7!) + F(9)) - 2))) \\
 39793 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-((F(9) - (7!/9))) + F(F(3)))) \\
 39793 &:= ((F(3!))! - (-((F(9) - (7!/9))) + F(F(3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39794 &:= (((F(3!))! + ((F(9) - (7!/9)))) \times F(F(F(4)))) \\ 39796 &:= (((F(3) + F(9)) - (7!/9)) + (F(6))!) \\ 39798 &:= (((3!)/(-9)) - ((F(7) \times F(9)) - 8!)) \\ 39802 &:= (-(((F(3)^9) - 8!)) - ((0! + 2))!) \\ 39803 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) - 0!) + 3!) \\ 39804 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) + 04)) \\ 39805 &:= (-(((F(3)^9) - 8!)) - F(-((0! - (5)))))) \\ 39806 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(9) + ((80 \times 6)))) \\ 39807 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) + ((0 \times 7))!) \\ 39808 &:= -(((F(3)^9) - ((8 \times 0) + 8))!) \\ 39809 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) - ((0 \times 9))!) \\ 39810 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) - 1) - 0!) \\ 39813 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) + 1) - 3!) \\ 39814 &:= (-(((F(3)^9) - 8!)) + (F((1 \times 4))!)) \\ 39816 &:= (((F(3)^9) - 8!) \times (-1)) + F(6) \\ 39822 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 + F((8 \times 2)))/2)) \\ 39823 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 \times F((8 + 2))) + F(3))) \\ 39824 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) - ((2^4)))) \\ 39825 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9!/8!) \times F((2 \times 5)))) \\ 39826 &:= ((F(F(3)) - (9 \times F((8 + 2)))) + (F(6))!) \\ 39827 &:= ((-((3 \times 9)) + 8!) + (-2) \times F(F(7))) \\ 39829 &:= (F(F(-((3 - 9)))) + ((8! - (2^9)))) \\ 39830 &:= -(((F((3! + 9)) - 8!) - ((3! - 0!))!) \\ 39832 &:= (-(((F(3)^9) - 8!)) + ((F(3) + 2))!) \\ 39833 &:= -((((3!))! - F((F(9) - F(8)))) - (F((3 + 3))!)) \\ 39834 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) - F(3)) - 4!) \\ 39835 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - (F(8) \times (-3))) \times 5)) \\ 39836 &:= (-(((3! - F(9)) + (8^3))) + (F(6))!) \\ 39838 &:= -((3! - ((F(9) \times (-8) - 3!) + 8!)) \\ 39839 &:= (((-3) + F(9)) + 8!) - (F(3)^9) \\ 39840 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((-9) + F(8)) \times 40) \\ 39841 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(9) - ((8^{F(4)} + 1)))) \\ 39842 &:= (-(((F(3)^9) - 8!)) + F((F(4)^2))) \\ 39843 &:= ((3^9) + ((8!/4) \times F(3))) \\ 39844 &:= ((3^9) - ((-8!) - F(F(4)))/F(F(4))) \end{aligned}$$

- 39845 := ((F(3!))! - ((98 - F(4)) × 5))
39846 := (((((3!)! × (-9)) - (F(8))) + F(4!)) - F(F(6)))
39847 := -((((F(3)⁹) - 8!) - (F(4) × F(7))))
39848 := ((3! + F(9)) - ((8^{F(4)}) - 8!))
39850 := ((F(3!))! - (-F(9) + (F(8) × ((5 - 0!)!)))
39852 := ((F(3!))! - ((9!/8!) × 52))
39854 := ((F((3 + 9)) + 8!) - F((5 × F(4))))
39855 := ((F(3!))! - ((98 - 5) × 5))
39862 := -((((F(3!) + (9 - 8!)) + (F(F(6))²)))
39863 := (((((3!)! / (-9)) + 8!) - F((F(6) + 3!)))
39864 := (((3! × (-9 × 8)) + (F(6)!)) - (4!))
39865 := ((F(3!))! - (9 + ((F(8) × F(F(6))) + (5))))
39866 := ((F(3!) × F(9)) + ((8! - (6)) - 6!))
39867 := ((F(F(3)) × ((F(9) + 8!) - 6!)) + F(F(7)))
39868 := (-((F(3) + 9)) - ((F(8) × F(F(6))) - 8!))
39869 := ((F(3!))! - (9 + ((F(8) - F(6)) × F(9))))
39870 := ((F(3!))! - (9 + (F(8) × F((7 + 0!))))))
39871 := (((F(3!) × (-9)) + 8!) - F((F(7) + 1)))
39872 := (F(3!) × (-((F(9) + F(8)) - 7!) + F(2)))
39873 := (((((3! + F(9)) + 8!) + F(F(7))) - 3!!))
39875 := ((F(3!) × (-((F(9) + F(8)) - 7!))) - (5))
39876 := (-F(3) + ((F((9!/8!)) × (-F(7))) + (F(6)!))
39877 := ((F(3!))! - (((-9) - F(8)) × (-7) + F(F(7))))
39878 := (((F(3) × (-9 + 8)) × F(7)) + 8!)
39879 := ((F(F(3))⁹)! + ((8! - (F(7) × F(9))))))

39880 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 0
39881 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 1
39882 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 2
39883 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 3
39884 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 4
39885 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 5
39886 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 6
39887 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 7
39888 := -F(3!) × (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 8

$$\begin{aligned} 39889 &:= -F(3!) \times (F(9) + F(8)) + 8! + 9 \\ 39891 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - F(8)) \times (F(9) - 1))) \\ 39893 &:= ((3!)! + ((9 + 8!) - (F(9)^{F(3)}))) \\ 39893 &:= ((3!)! + ((9 + 8!) - (F(9)^{F(3)}))) \\ 39897 &:= (((((3!)! \times (-F(9)))/(-8)) + 9) \times F(7)) \\ 39898 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 \times F(8)) + F((F(9) - F(8))))) \\ 39899 &:= ((F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(9) - 8)) - (9!/(-9))) \\ 39905 &:= (((F(F(3!))!)/(9 + 9)!) + 0!) \times 5 \\ 39906 &:= (-((3! \times ((F(9) + F(9)) + 0!))) + (F(6))!) \\ 39912 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(9) \times ((9 + 1) + 2))) \\ 39913 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(9) - (F((9 - 1))^{F(3)}))) \\ 39914 &:= (F((3! + 9)) + (F(9)^{F(1 \times 4)})) \\ 39915 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((9 \times 9) \times 1) \times 5)) \\ 39917 &:= -((F(3!) + ((9 - F(9)) \times F(17)))) \\ 39918 &:= -(((3! \times ((F(9) + F(9)) - 1)) - 8!)) \\ 39921 &:= (-(399) + (F(((2 + 1)!)!))! \\ 39922 &:= (((((3!)! \times (-9)) + F(9)) + F(((2 + 2)!)!)) \\ 39923 &:= (-(399 - 2)) + (F(3!))! \\ 39925 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((9 \times 9) - 2) \times 5)) \\ 39926 &:= (((((3!)! + (F(9) + F(9)))/(-2)) + (F(6))!) \\ 39933 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((9 + F(9)) \times (3 \times 3))) \\ 39934 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) \times F(9)) + F(3))/F(4))) \\ 39935 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - 9) - (-3 \times 5!))) \\ 39937 &:= (-((3! + (9!/(-9)))) - F((F(3) \times 7))) \\ 39938 &:= ((-(((F(3) + 9) \times F(9))) - F(3!)) + 8!) \\ 39941 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times (F(9) \times (-9))) + (F(4!) - 1)) \\ 39942 &:= (((F(3!) + F(9)) \times (-9)) + ((4 \times 2)!) \\ 39943 &:= ((F(3!))! - F(((9/9) + F((4 + 3)))) \\ 39944 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times (9 + F(F(4)))) + F(F(4)))) \\ 39945 &:= ((F(3!))! - (((F(9) - 9) \times F(4)) \times 5)) \\ 39946 &:= ((3 - F(((9 + 9) - 4))) + (F(6))!) \\ 39947 &:= ((F(3!))! - (9 + ((F(9) - (F(4))!) \times F(7)))) \\ 39948 &:= (((3 \times F(9)) - 9) \times (-4)) + 8! \\ 39949 &:= (((F(3!))! - (99)) + (F((F(4))!) \times (-F(9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$39951 := ((F(3!))! - ((-9) + F((9 + 5))) + 1))$$

$$39952 := ((F(3!))! - ((-9) + F((9 + 5))) \times F(2)))$$

$$39953 := ((F(3!))! - (F(9) + ((9 - 5!) \times (-3))))$$

$$39954 := -(((3! + (9!/(-9)))) + (5! \times F(4))))$$

$$39955 := (((3 + F(9)) \times 9) \times 5!) - (5))$$

$$39956 := (((F(3!) - F(9)) \times (9 + 5)) + (F(6)!))$$

$$39957 := ((F(3!))! - ((9 \times F(9)) + (57)))$$

$$39958 := (((3! + 9) - F((9 + 5))) + 8!)$$

$$39960 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 0$$

$$39961 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 1$$

$$39962 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 2$$

$$39963 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 3$$

$$39964 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 4$$

$$39965 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 5$$

$$39966 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 6$$

$$39967 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 7$$

$$39968 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 8$$

$$39969 := -(3! + F(9)) \times 9 + F(6)! + 9$$

$$39970 := ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) - 9) \times (F(7) + 0!)))$$

$$39973 := ((F(3!) \times ((-9) - F(9)) + 7!) - 3)$$

$$39974 := ((-3) - (9!/(-9))) - (7^{F(4)})$$

$$39975 := (((F(3!) - (9!/(-9))) - F(F(7))) - 5!)$$

$$39976 := (F(F(3)) \times (((-9) - F(9)) + 7!) \times F(6))$$

$$39977 := -(((3!)! - ((9!/9) + F((7 + 7))))))$$

$$39978 := (F(3) - (((-9) - F(9)) + 7!) \times (-8))$$

$$39979 := ((F(3!))! - ((99 + F(F(7))) + 9))$$

$$39980 := -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 0$$

$$39981 := -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 1$$

$$39982 := -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 2$$

$$39983 := -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 3$$

$$39984 := -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 4$$

$$39985 := -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39986 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 6 \\
 39987 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 7 \\
 39988 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 8 \\
 39989 &:= -(F(F(3)) + 9) \times F(9) + 8! + 9 \\
 \\
 39990 &:= ((3!)! + ((F(9) \times ((F(9) \times F(9)) - 0!))) \\
 39993 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((9 \times F(9)) + F(F((9 - 3)))))) \\
 39993 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((9 \times F(9)) + F(F((9 - 3)))))) \\
 39994 &:= ((F(3!)! - (-F(9)) + (9 \times (F(9) + (F(4)!)))))) \\
 39995 &:= ((F(3!)! - ((99 - F(9)) \times 5)) \\
 39996 &:= (-(((3 \times 9) + 9) \times 9) + (F(6))!) \\
 39997 &:= ((F(3!)! - (((9 \times 9) + 9) + F(F(7)))))) \\
 39998 &:= (((F(3) - F(9)) \times 9) - F(9)) + 8! \\
 40024 &:= ((F((F((F(4))!) + 0!)^{0!+2}) + ((F(4)!))!) \\
 40032 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! + 0!) \times F((3! \times 2)))) \\
 40033 &:= (-((F(4!) - 0!) - ((-((0! - 3!))! \times (-3!))) \\
 40034 &:= ((F(((F(4))! + 0!) \times (-0!) - F(F(3!)))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 40043 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (((0! + 0!)^{F(F(4)!)} + F(F(3!)))))) \\
 40045 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (F(((0! + 0!) + F((F(4)!))) \times 5)) \\
 40046 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (0! + (F((0! + (F(4)!)) \times F(F(6)))))) \\
 40047 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (F(((0! + 0!)^{F(4)}) \times F(7))) \\
 40048 &:= ((-F((F(4)^{0!+0!})) \times F((F(4)!)) + 8!) \\
 40049 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (-0! + (F((F(04))!) \times F(9)))) \\
 40056 &:= (-((4! + ((0! + 0!) \times 5!)) + (F(6))!) \\
 40062 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (((0! + 0!)^{F(6)} + 2)) \\
 40063 &:= ((-4! - F(F((0! + 06)))) + (F(3!)!) \\
 40064 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - (((0! + 0!)^6) \times 4)) \\
 40066 &:= ((F(F(4)) - ((0! + 0!)^{F(6)})) + (F(6))!) \\
 40067 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - ((-0! + F(F(06))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 40068 &:= (4 - (((0! + 0!)^{F(6)} - 8!)) \\
 40073 &:= -(((F(((F(4))! + 0!)) - (-0! - F(F(7)))) - (F(3!)!)) \\
 40074 &:= (((F(((F(4))! + 0!)) \times (-0!)) - F(F(7))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 40078 &:= ((-((F(4)^{0!+0!})) - F(F(7))) + 8!) \\
 40079 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - ((-0! + F(F(07))) + 9)) \\
 40083 &:= ((-4) - F(F(((0 - 0!) + 8)))) + (F(3!)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 40084** := ((F((F(4)!))! - (F(F(((0 - 0!) + 8))) + F(4)))
40085 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! + 0!) + F((8 + 5))))
40086 := -(((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(((0 - 0!) + 8)))) - (F(6)!))
40087 := (((4 × 0) + 08)! - F(F(7)))
40089 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (-((0! + 0!) + F(-(F(8) - F(9))))))
40093 := (((F((F(4)!))! - F(F(-((0! + 0!) - 9)))) + 3!)
40096 := ((4 × (-0!) - F((0! + 9))) + (F(6)!))
40097 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (((0 - 0!) - 9) + F(F(7))))
40104 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! - F(10)) × (-4)))
40104 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! - F(10)) × (-4)))
40124 := (-(((F((F(4)! + 0!)) + 1)²) + (F((F(4)!))!))
40127 := ((40 + (F(((1 + 2)!))!)) - F(F(7)))
40136 := (((4! - 0!) - ((1 + 3)!)) × (-F(6)))
40139 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (0! + ((-1 + F(F(3!))) × 9)))
40143 := (((F((F(4)!))! - 0!) - ((1 + F(F((F(4)!))) × F(3!)))
40144 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (-((0! + 1) - 4!)) × F((F(4)!)))
40145 := (((F((F(4)!))! - F(((0! + 1) + F((F(4)!)))) - 5!)
40149 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (0! + ((1 + 4) × F(9))))
40153 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (-0! + (F(F((1 + 5))) × F(3!))))
40158 := ((F(F((F(4)!)) × (-0! + 1)) - (5! - 8!))
40160 := ((F((F(4)!))! - 0160)
40164 := (((4! + 0!) + 1) × (-6) + (F((F(4)!))!))
40165 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! + F((1 + F(6)))) + 5!))
40166 := (((F(4)! + 0!) × (-1 - F(F(6)))) + (F(6)!))
40167 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (-0! + ((1 + F(F(6))) × 7)))
40168 := -((F((4! / (0! + 1))) + (F(6) - 8!))
40173 := ((-F(4) - F(((0 - 1) + F(7)))) + (F(3)!))
40174 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((-0! + F((-1 + F(7)))) + F(4)))
40176 := ((4! × (01 - 7)) + (F(6)!))
40177 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((0! + 1) - F(7)) × F(7)))
40178 := ((F(F(4)) - F(((0 - 1) + F(7)))) + 8!)
40184 := (-((F((4! / (0! + 1))) - 8!)) + F((F(4)!))
40187 := -((((4 + 01)! - 8!) + F(7))
40188 := ((4 × (0! - F((1 + 8)))) + 8!)
40192 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! + 1)⁹⁻²))

$$40193 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (0! + (F(-((1 - 9))) \times 3!)))$$

$$40194 := -((((4 + 0!)! - (-((1 - 9)))!) + (F(4)!))$$

$$40200 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 0$$

$$40201 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 1$$

$$40202 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 2$$

$$40203 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 3$$

$$40204 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 4$$

$$40205 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 5$$

$$40206 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 6$$

$$40207 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 7$$

$$40208 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 8$$

$$40209 := -(4 + 0!)! + F((2 + 0!)!) + 9$$

$$40210 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (02 \times F(10)))$$

$$40215 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (021 \times 5))$$

$$40216 := ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-F((0! + ((2 + 1)!)))) + (F(6)!))$$

$$40217 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((-0!) - (((2 + 1)!)))/(-7)))$$

$$40218 := ((-F(4)) \times F((0! + F(((2 + 1)!)))) + 8!)$$

$$40219 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((0! - ((2 + 1) \times F(9))))))$$

$$40224 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((02 + 2) \times 4!))$$

$$40225 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((0! + ((2 + 2)!)) - 5!)))$$

$$40227 := ((-4) + (F(((0! + 2)!))!) - F((-2) + F(7)))$$

$$40229 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (02 + F((2 + 9))))$$

$$40230 := (((((F(4)!)/F((0! + 2)!)) - (F(3)!)) \times (-0!))$$

$$40231 := -((((((F(4)!)/F((0! + 2)!)) - (F(3)!)) - 1))$$

$$40232 := -((((((F(4)!)/F((0! + 2)!)) - (F(3)!)) - 2))$$

$$40233 := (-(((4! - 0!) + (2^{3!}))) + (F(3)!))$$

$$40234 := ((-((40 \times 2)) + (F(3)!)) - (F(4)!))$$

$$40235 := ((-((40 \times 2)) + (F(3)!)) - (5))$$

$$40236 := ((-4) \times F((02^3))) + (F(6)!)$$

$$40237 := -((((((F(4)!)/F((0! + 2)!)) - (F(3)!)) - 7))$$

$$40238 := ((-((40 \times 2)) - F(3)) + 8!)$$

$$40239 := ((-((4! \times (0! + 2))) + (F(3)!)) - 9)$$

$$40240 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!)) + 0$$

$$40241 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 1$$

$$40242 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 2$$

$$40243 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 3$$

$$40244 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 4$$

$$40245 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 5$$

$$40246 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 6$$

$$40247 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 7$$

$$40248 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 8$$

$$40249 := -40 \times 2 + F(F(4)!) + 9$$

$$40252 := ((F((F(4)!)!))! - (F(((0! + 2))!) + (5!/2)))$$

$$40253 := (-(((4! \times (0! + 2)) - (5))) + (F(3!)!))$$

$$40254 := ((F((F(4)!)!))! - ((0! + (2 \times 5)) \times (F(4)!)!))$$

$$40255 := ((F((F(4)!)!))! - (F((02 + 5)) \times 5))$$

$$40256 := (-((4^{-02+5})) + (F(6)!)$$

$$40257 := ((F((F(4)!)!))! - ((0! + F((2 \times 5))) + (7)))$$

$$40258 := ((F(F(4)) \times (0! - (2^5))) + 8!)$$

$$40259 := ((F((F(4)!)!))! - (02 + 59))$$

$$40261 := (((((4 + 0!)!)/(-2)) + (F(6)!) + 1)$$

$$40262 := (((((4 + 0!)!)/(-2)) + (F(6)!) + 2)$$

$$40263 := (((((4 + 0!)!)/(-2)) + (F(6)!) + 3)$$

$$40264 := ((-((40 \times 2)) + (F(6)!) + (4!))$$

$$40265 := (((((4 + 0!)!)/(-2)) + (F(6)!) + (5))$$

$$40266 := (((((4 + 0!)!)/(-2)) + (F(6)!) + 6)$$

$$40267 := ((-40) + ((2 + 6)!) - F(7))$$

$$40269 := (((((4 + 0!)!)/(-2)) + (F(6)!) + 9)$$

$$40271 := -((((F(4)!) + 0!)^2) - ((7 + 1)!)!))$$

$$40272 := ((4! \times (0 - 2)) + ((7 + F(2))!))$$

$$40273 := (F(F(F(4))) - (((0! + 2))! - (7!)) \times F(3!))$$

$$40274 := ((-40) + ((F(2) + (7))!) - (F(4)!)$$

$$40275 := ((-40) + ((F(2) + (7))!) - (5))$$

$$40277 := ((F((F(4)!)!))! - (0! + ((F(2) - (7)) \times (-7))))$$

$$40279 := (((((4 \times 02))! - (7)) - F(9))$$

$$40280 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 0$$

$$40281 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 1$$

$$40282 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 2$$

$$40283 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 3$$

$$40284 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 4$$

$$40285 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 5$$

$$40286 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 6$$

$$40287 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 7$$

$$40288 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 8$$

$$40289 := -40 \times F(2) + 8! + 9$$

$$40291 := ((F((F(4)!))!) - (029 \times 1))$$

$$40292 := ((F((F(4)!))!) - (0! + (29 - 2)))$$

$$40294 := ((- (4!) + ((0! - ((2 - 9))))!) - F(F(4)))$$

$$40297 := -(((4! - 0!) + ((F(2) - 9) \times 7!))$$

$$40299 := -((F((4 \times 02)) + (9! / (-9))))$$

$$40300 := ((F((F(4)!))!) - (- (0!) + F(((3! + 0!) + 0!))))$$

$$40301 := ((F((F(4)!))!) - ((- (0!) + F(F(3!))) - 01))$$

$$40302 := ((- (4!) + (F((03)!))!) + ((0! + 2)!)$$

$$40303 := ((- ((4! + 0!)) + (F(3!))!) + F((03)!))$$

$$40304 := (F((F(4)!)) + (((((0! + 3!) + 0!))! - (4!))))$$

$$40304 := (F((F(4)!)) + (((((0! + 3!) + 0!))! - (4!))))$$

$$40305 := ((- ((4! - 0!)) + (F(3!))!) + F((0! + (5))))$$

$$40306 := ((F(F(4)) \times (- (0! + 3!))) + (F(06)!))$$

$$40307 := (((4! / 03)! - F(07))$$

$$40309 := -(((F(F(4)) - (((0! + 3!) + 0!))!) + 9))$$

$$40311 := (((F((F(4)!)) + 0!) - (F(3!))!) \times (- (1 \times 1)))$$

$$40312 := (((4! / 03)! - F(((1 + 2)!))$$

$$40314 := (((F(4)! \times (-0!)) + (((3 - 1) \times 4)!))$$

$$40318 := ((- (4) + F(03)) + ((1 \times 8)!)$$

$$40322 := ((F(4) - 0!) + (((3 \times 2) + 2)!)$$

$$40323 := (F(4) + (((0 \times 3) + 2)^3)!)$$

$$40330 := 4 + 03! + F(3!) + 0$$

$$40331 := 4 + 03! + F(3!) + 1$$

$$40332 := 4 + 03! + F(3!) + 2$$

$$40333 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 3$$

$$40334 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 4$$

$$40335 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 5$$

$$40336 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 6$$

$$40337 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 7$$

$$40338 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 8$$

$$40339 := 4 + 03! + F(3!)! + 9$$

$$40340 := (((-4) - 0!) + (F(3!)!)) + (4! + 0!)$$

$$40341 := ((4! - 03) + (F((4 - 1)!))!)$$

$$40342 := ((4! - F(03)) + ((4 \times 2)!))$$

$$40345 := ((4! + 0!) + (((3! - F(4)) + (5)))!)$$

$$40346 := (((F(4) - 0!) \times F((3 + 4))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$40347 := ((40 + ((F(3)^{F(4)}))!) - F(7))$$

$$40349 := (((-4) - 0!) + ((F(3)^{F(4)}))!) + F(9))$$

$$40350 := ((4! + (03)!) + (F((5 + 0!)!))!)$$

$$40351 := (((4! + 0!) + 3!) + (F((5 + 1)!))!)$$

$$40352 := ((4 + ((0! + 3!)!)) \times F((5 - 2)!))$$

$$40353 := (((4! + 0!) + F(3!)) + ((5 + 3)!))$$

$$40354 := ((40 - 3!) + ((5 + F(4))!))$$

$$40356 := (((4 \times 0)! + 35) + (F(6))!)$$

$$40357 := ((4! + ((03 + 5)!)) + F(7))$$

$$40359 := (((4 + 0!) + ((3 + 5)!)) + F(9))$$

$$40360 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 0$$

$$40361 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 1$$

$$40362 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 2$$

$$40363 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 3$$

$$40364 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 4$$

$$40365 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 5$$

$$40366 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 6$$

$$40367 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 7$$

$$40368 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 8$$

$$40369 := (4 + 0!) \times F(3!) + F(6)! + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40370 &:= (((4! + 0!) \times F(3)) + ((7 + 0!)!)) \\
 40371 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0! + 3) \times F(7)) - 1)) \\
 40373 &:= (-(F(4)) + (((0! + 3!) + 7!) \times F(3!))) \\
 40374 &:= ((F(4))! + (F((03)!) \times (7! + (F(4))!))) \\
 40375 &:= (F((4 + (03)!) + ((F(7) - (5))!)) \\
 40376 &:= (((4 + 03) + 7!) \times F(6)) \\
 40377 &:= (((4 \times 0))! - (F(3!) \times (-(7) - 7!))) \\
 40378 &:= ((F(4) + F((03 + 7))) + 8!) \\
 40379 &:= ((4! + 0!) - ((F(3!) \times (-7!)) - F(9))) \\
 \\
 40380 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 0 \\
 40381 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 1 \\
 40382 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 2 \\
 40383 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 3 \\
 40384 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 4 \\
 40385 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 5 \\
 40386 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 6 \\
 40387 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 7 \\
 40388 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 8 \\
 40389 &:= (4 + 0)!/F(3) + 8! + 9 \\
 \\
 40390 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! + ((F(3) \times F(9)) + 0!))) \\
 40391 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (((0! + 3!)! + 9)) - 1) \\
 40392 &:= ((4! \times 03) + ((9 - F(2))!)) \\
 40393 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (((0! + 3!)! + 9) \times F(3!))) \\
 40394 &:= ((-(((F(4))! + 0!)) + (F(3!)! + (9^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 40395 &:= (((4 + 0!)! + (F(3!)!)) - (9 \times 5)) \\
 40396 &:= (((40 + F(3)) + F(9)) + (F(6))!) \\
 40397 &:= ((4 + 0!) - (F(3!) \times (-(9) - 7!))) \\
 40398 &:= (((F(4) - 0!) \times 39) + 8!) \\
 40401 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + F((F(4))!))^{0!+1})) \\
 40402 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + 40) \times 2)) \\
 40403 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (-0! + (4 \times F(F((03)!)))) \\
 40404 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F(F(((0! + (4)) + 0!))) \times 4))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 40404 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(F((0! + (4)) + 0!))) × 4))
- 40405 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (0! + (4 × F(F((0! + (5)))))))
- 40406 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((0! + (4))! - F((0! + F(6))))))
- 40409 := (F(((F(4)! + (0! + (4)))) + (-((0! - 9)))!)
- 40410 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((0! + F((F(4)!)) × 10))
- 40411 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (((0! - F(4)) - F(11))))
- 40412 := (((4! - 0!) × 4) + (F(((1 + 2)!))!)
- 40413 := (((4! - 0!) × 4) + 1) + (F(3!)!)
- 40415 := ((-(4! + 0!)) + (F(((4 - 1)!))!)) + 5!
- 40416 := ((4! × 04) + (F((1 × 6)))!)
- 40417 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (0! + (F((F(4)!)) × (-1 + F(7))))))
- 40418 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (((0! - ((4 + 1)!)) + F(8))))
- 40419 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(04) × (-1 + F(9))))
- 40420 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((0! + (4)) × 20))
- 40422 := ((F(4) × F((0! + F((F(4)!)))) + (F((F((2 + 2)!))!))
- 40423 := (((((F(4)! + 0!)/(F(4)! + F(2))) + (F(3!)!)
- 40424 := ((F((F(4)!)) × F((0! + (F(4)!))) + (((2 × 4)!))
- 40425 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((04 × 2)) × 5))
- 40426 := ((F((F(4)!)) × F((0! + (F(4)!))) - (-2 - (F(6)!))
- 40427 := (((4 + 0!)! + (((4 × 2)! - F(7))))
- 40429 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (0! + ((4!/2) × 9)))
- 40430 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((0! + (4)) × (F(F(3!)) + 0!)))
- 40431 := (((((4 + 0!)! - F((F(4)!)) + (F(3!)!)) - 1)
- 40432 := (F((F(4)!)) × ((0! + (F(4)!)) × ((3!)! + 2)))
- 40433 := ((4! + F(((0! + (4)) + 3!))) + (F(3!)!)
- 40434 := (((((4 + 0!)! - (F(4)!)) + ((F(3)^{F(4)})!))
- 40436 := ((-4) + ((0! + (4))!)) + ((F(3) + (6))!)
- 40437 := ((-F(4) + ((0! + (4))!)) - (F(3!) × (-7!)))
- 40438 := (((4 + 0!) × 4!) - F(3)) + 8!
- 40439 := (((F(4)! + 0!) × F((4! + 3)))/F(9))
- 40446 := (F(4!)) + ((0 - F((4 × 4)) × 6))
- 40448 := (((4 + 0!)^{F(4)}) + F(4)) + 8!
- 40450 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((0! + F((F(4)!)) + (5! + 0!))))
- 40452 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((0! + (F(4)!)) + (5! - F(2))))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 40453 &:= (((F(4))! + 0!) \times (4! - (5))) + (F(3))! \\
 40454 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - ((0! - (45 \times F(4)))) \\
 40455 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(04) \times 5) + 5!)) \\
 40456 &:= ((4 \times F((04 + 5))) + (F(6))!) \\
 40457 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((04 + 5!) + F(7))) \\
 40458 &:= ((F(4) \times (0! + 45)) + 8!) \\
 40459 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(F((F(04))!)) \times 5) + F(9))) \\
 40460 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0! + (4)))! + F(F(6))) - 0!) \\
 40461 &:= (((F(4!)) + ((0! + (F(4))!))! - F(F(F(6)))) - 1) \\
 40462 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 04)) + (F(6))!) - 2) \\
 40463 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 04)) + (F(6))!) - F(F(3))) \\
 40465 &:= (((4! + ((0 \times 4))!) + (F(6))!) + 5!) \\
 40466 &:= ((-4) + ((0! + 4!) \times 6)) + (F(6))! \\
 40467 &:= (((((4 + 0))! - F(4!)) / (-F(6))) \times 7) \\
 40469 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + (4)) + F((F(F(6)) - 9)))) \\
 40470 &:= (((F(4))! \times (0! + 4!)) + ((7 + 0))!) \\
 40471 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + (F(4))!) + F((F(7) - 1)))) \\
 40472 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((F(04))!) + F((F(7) - F(2))))) \\
 40473 &:= (((40 \times 4) - 7) + (F(3))!) \\
 40474 &:= (((((4 + 0))! - F(F(4))) \times (7^{F(4)})) \\
 40475 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((04)! + (7)) \times 5)) \\
 40476 &:= (((F(4) \times 04) \times F(7)) + (F(6))!) \\
 40477 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((0! + (4 + 7))) + F(7))) \\
 40478 &:= -((F(4) + (((0! - 4!) \times 7) - 8!)) \\
 40479 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0 - 4!) \times (-7)) - 9)) \\
 \\
 40490 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 0 \\
 40491 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 1 \\
 40492 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 2 \\
 40493 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 3 \\
 40494 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 4 \\
 40495 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 5 \\
 40496 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 6 \\
 40497 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 7 \\
 40498 &:= F(F(4))! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40499 &:= F(F(4)!)! + (0! + 4) \times F(9) + 9 \\
 40503 &:= (F(F((F(4)! + 0!))) - (50 - (F(3!)!)) \\
 40504 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (F((0! + (5))) \times (- (0! - 4!)))) \\
 40504 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (F((0! + (5))) \times (- (0! - 4!)))) \\
 40509 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (F(F((0! + (5)))) \times 09)) \\
 40512 &:= ((4! \times F((0! + (5)))) + (F(((1 + 2)!)!)) \\
 40513 &:= (((4! \times F((0! + (5)))) + 1) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 40519 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (F(F((0! + (5 + 1)))) - F(9))) \\
 40520 &:= ((40 \times 5) + (F((2 + 0!)!)!)) \\
 40524 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + ((0! - (52)) \times (-4))) \\
 40526 &:= -((F((F((F(4)!) + 0!)) + ((5! \times (-2)) - (F(6)!)!)) \\
 40527 &:= ((- (4!) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + (- (2) + F(F(7)))) \\
 40529 &:= ((- (4!) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + F(F(- ((2 - 9)))) \\
 40532 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + ((0! + (5 \times F(F(3!)))) \times 2)) \\
 40533 &:= ((- (F(4)) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + (3!^3)) \\
 40534 &:= ((- (F(F(4))) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + (3!^{F(4)})) \\
 40535 &:= ((- (((4! + 0!) - 5!)) + (F(3!)!) + 5!) \\
 40536 &:= (F(4!) - (((0! + (5))^{3!}) / F(6))) \\
 40537 &:= ((- (4!) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + (F(3!) + F(F(7)))) \\
 40538 &:= -((4! - (((0! + 5!) \times F(3)) + 8!)) \\
 40539 &:= (F(F((F(4)! + 0!))) - ((5 - (F(3!)!) + 9)) \\
 40542 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + ((- ((0! - 5!)) - F((F(4)!)!) \times 2)) \\
 40543 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (- (0!) + ((5! - F((F(4)!)!) \times F(3)))) \\
 40544 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + ((F(4)!)^{F(4)})) \\
 40545 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (05 \times 45)) \\
 40546 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (- ((0! - 5!)) - (F(4)!)!) + (F(6)!) \\
 40547 &:= (((4 + 0!)^5) - (F(4)!) \times F(7)) \\
 40548 &:= ((F(4)!) \times ((0! + F((5 \times 4))) - 8)) \\
 40549 &:= ((- (4) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + (F((4 + 9)))) \\
 40552 &:= -(((F(F(F(4))) - (F((0! + (5))))!) - (F(F((5 + 2)))))) \\
 40553 &:= (F(F((F(4) - 0!) + (5))) + (((5 + 3)!)!)) \\
 40554 &:= ((F(4)!) \times (- ((0! + (5)) - F((5 \times 4)))) \\
 40555 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (((05)! + 5!) - (5))) \\
 40556 &:= (((- (4) + (05)!) + 5!) + (F(6)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40557 &:= ((4 + (F(((0 \times 5)! + (5))))!) + F(F(7))) \\ 40558 &:= (((F(4)^05) - (5)) + 8!) \\ 40559 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (- (0!) + (5! \times F(F(-(5 - 9)))))) \\ \\ 40560 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 0 \\ 40561 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 1 \\ 40562 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 2 \\ 40563 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 3 \\ 40564 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 4 \\ 40565 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 5 \\ 40566 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 6 \\ 40567 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 7 \\ 40568 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 8 \\ 40569 &:= -(-F(4) + 0!) \times 5! + F(6)! + 9 \\ \\ 40571 &:= (((F(4!)/F((0! + (5)))) \times 7) - 1) \\ 40572 &:= ((F(4!)/F((0! + (5)))) \times (7 \times F(2))) \\ 40573 &:= (((F(4!)/F((0! + (5)))) \times 7) + F(F(3))) \\ 40574 &:= (((F(4!)/F((0! + (5)))) \times 7) + F(F(4))) \\ 40576 &:= (((F(4) - 0!)^5) + 7!) \times F(6) \\ 40577 &:= ((4! + (((0 \times 5)! + (7))))!) + F(F(7)) \\ 40578 &:= (((4! + ((0 \times 5)!)) + F(F(7))) + 8!) \\ 40579 &:= -(((F((F(4)!)) - (F((0! + (5))))!) - ((F(F(7)) + F(9)))))) \\ 40582 &:= -((F((F(4)!)) + (-((0! + (5))) \times F((F(8) - F(2)))))) \\ 40583 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times (0! + 5!)) + (F(8))) + (F(3)!)) \\ 40584 &:= (((F(4) - 0!) \times 5!) + 8!) + 4! \\ 40586 &:= (-4) + (F(-(((0 \times 5)! - F(8)))) \times 6) \\ 40587 &:= ((F(4!) - ((0! + (5))))!) - ((F(8) + 7!)) \\ 40588 &:= -((((F(4)!))! - ((0! + F((-5) + F(8)))) + 8!)) \\ 40589 &:= ((-F(4) + (F((0! + (5))))!) - (-8 \times F(9))) \\ 40590 &:= ((F(4)! \times F(-(((0 \times 5)! + F((9 - 0!)))))) \\ 40591 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F((0! + (5))) \times F(9)) - 1)) \\ 40592 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((0! - 5) \times F(9)) \times (-2)) \\ 40593 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + (F((0! + (5))))!) - (-F(9) \times F(3!)) \\ 40594 &:= ((F(F(4)) + (F((0! + (5))))!) - (-F(9) \times F((F(4)!))) \end{aligned}$$

- 40595 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((0! + 5!) + F(9)) + 5!))
40596 := ((F(4)! × (0! + F(((5 + 9) + 6))))
40597 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-((0! - (5 × 9))) + F(F(7))))
40598 := ((F(4)! + ((F((0! + (5))) × F(9)) + 8!))
40599 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(-((0! - (5)))) - F(9)) × (-9)))
40602 := ((-F(F(4))) - F((-0! + F(F(6)))) × (-((0! + 2)!))
40603 := (((F(4)! × F((-0! + F(F(6)))))) + F((0! + 3!)))
40604 := (F((F(4)! + ((0! + F((F(F(6)) - 0!))) × (F(4)!))
40604 := (F((F(4)! + ((0! + F((F(F(6)) - 0!))) × (F(4)!))
40606 := ((F(((F(4)! + 0!)) × (F(F(6)) + 0!)) + (F(6)!))
40607 := (F(4!) + (((0 - 6!) - 0!) - 7!))
40608 := (F(4!) + ((0 - 6!) × 08))
40609 := (F(4!) + ((0! + (6! × (0! - 9))))
40613 := ((4! - 0!) - (F((F(F(6)) - 1)) × (-3!)))
40614 := ((-4) - F((-0! + F(F(6)))) × (-1) × (F(4)!))
40616 := (F(4!) + ((0! - 6!) × F((1 × 6))))
40620 := ((F(4)! × (-((0! - (6)) - F(20))))
40623 := ((F(4!) - 0!) - ((6! - 2) × F(3!)))
40624 := ((F((F(4)!)) × ((0! - 6!) + F(2))) + F(4!))
40625 := (F(((F(4)! + 0!)) × ((6 - F(2))⁵))
40626 := ((-((F(4)!)) - F((-0! + F(F(6)))) × (F(2) × (-6)))
40630 := (40 - (-6) × F((F(F(3!)) - 0!)))
40631 := (((4! × F((0! + (6)))) + (F(3!))!) - 1)
40632 := ((4! × F((0! + (6)))) + (F((3 × 2)))!)
40633 := ((F(4!) + 0!) - ((6! - 3) × F(3!)))
40634 := (((4! × F((0! + (6)))) + (F(3!))!) + F(F(4)))
40635 := (((40 × F(6)) + (F(3!))!) - (5))
40636 := (-F(F(4))) + ((F((-0! + F(F(6)))) + F(3!)) × 6))
40637 := (((4 × F(F(06))) + (F(3!))!) + F(F(7)))
40638 := (((40 × F(6)) - F(3)) + 8!))
40639 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! - (F(6) × (3! + F(9))))))
40640 := (F((F(4)!)) × (((0! + (6)))! + 40))
40641 := (((40 × F(6)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + 1)
40642 := (((40 × F(6)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + 2)
40643 := (((40 × F(6)) + F(4)) + (F(3!))!))

$$\begin{aligned}
 40644 &:= ((F(4))! \times ((0! + F(6)) + F((4! - (4)))))) \\
 40645 &:= (((F(4))! \times F((-0! + F(F(6)))))) + F((F(F(4)) \times 5))) \\
 40646 &:= (((40 \times F(6)) + (F(4))!) + (F(6))!) \\
 40647 &:= (((40 \times F(6)) + (F((F(4))!))!) + 7) \\
 40648 &:= (F(4!)) + (((0! - 6!) + (4)) \times 8) \\
 40649 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (-0! + (6 \times F(-((4! - F(9))))))) \\
 40653 &:= (-((F(4) \times ((0! + F(6)) - 5!))) + (F(3))!) \\
 40654 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0 - (F(6))!)/(-5!)) - F(F(4)))) \\
 40655 &:= ((4 \times (-0!) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5^5)) \\
 40656 &:= (F(4!)) + (((0! - 6!) + (5)) \times F(6)) \\
 40657 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (-0! + ((F(F(6)) + (5)) \times F(7)))) \\
 40658 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((0 - (F(6))!)/(-5!)) + 8!)) \\
 40662 &:= ((F(4))! \times (F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) + (6 \times 2)) \\
 40663 &:= (((F(4))! + ((F(06))! - F((F(6) + 3!)))) \\
 40664 &:= (((40 \times F(6)) + (F(6))!) + (4!)) \\
 40665 &:= (F((F(4))!)) + ((0! + (F(6))!) - ((F(6))!/(-5!))) \\
 40667 &:= (((((4 + 0!))! - 6) + (F(6))!) + F(F(7))) \\
 40668 &:= (((4! + F((0! + F(6)))) \times 6) + 8!) \\
 40670 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! - (6)) \times (-70))) \\
 40672 &:= ((-((4! + 0!)) + (F(6))!) + (F((7 \times 2)))) \\
 40673 &:= ((-4!) + (F(06))!) + F((7 \times F(3))) \\
 40674 &:= ((-((4! - 0!)) + (F(6))!) + F((7 \times F(F(4)))))) \\
 40675 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F(06))!) + F(F(7))) + 5!) \\
 40676 &:= ((F(4) + (-((0! - (6))))!) + (F(F(7)) + (F(6))!)) \\
 40677 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! - F(F(6))) + (F((7 + 7)))))) \\
 40679 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - ((0! - (6!/(-7 - 9)))))) \\
 \\
 40680 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 0 \\
 40681 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 1 \\
 40682 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 2 \\
 40683 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 3 \\
 40684 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 4 \\
 40685 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 5 \\
 40686 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 6 \\
 40687 &:= F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$40688 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 8$$

$$40689 := F(4) \times (-0! + 6)! + 8! + 9$$

$$40692 := ((F(4))! \times (F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) + (F(9)/2))$$

$$40693 := ((-4) + F(-((0! - (6 + 9)))) + (F(3)!))!$$

$$40694 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0! + F(F(6))) \times F(9))/F(F(4))))$$

$$40695 := ((-(F(4) - 0!) + (F(6))!) + (F((9 + 5))))$$

$$40696 := ((F(F(4)) \times (-0!) + (F(F(6)) \times 9)) + (F(6))!)$$

$$40697 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0! - (6)) + F(9)) \times F(7)))$$

$$40698 := (((F(4))! \times ((0! + (6)) \times 9)) + 8!)$$

$$40699 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! + ((F(6) + F(9)) \times 9)))$$

$$40703 := (((F(4))! + F((0! + F(7)))) + (F((03)!))!)$$

$$40704 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + F((F(7) + 0!))) + (F(4))!))$$

$$40704 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + F((F(7) + 0!))) + (F(4))!))$$

$$40705 := ((F((F(4))!) + (F((0! + F(7)))) + (F((0! + (5))))!)$$

$$40706 := (F((F(4))!) - ((-0!) - F((F(7) + 0!))) - (F(6))!)$$

$$40716 := ((F(4))! \times (F((0! + (7))) + F((-1 + F(F(6))))))$$

$$40718 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((0! + F(7))) + F((1 \times 8))))$$

$$40719 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((0! + (7))) \times 19))$$

$$40721 := ((4! + F((0! + F(7)))) + (F(((2 + 1)!))!)$$

$$40723 := (((4! + F((0! + F(7)))) + 2) + (F(3)!))!$$

$$40726 := ((407 - F(2)) + (F(6))!)$$

$$40727 := (407 + ((F(2) + (7)))!)$$

$$40728 := ((407 + F(2)) + 8!)$$

$$40729 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! + ((F(7) - F(2)) \times F(9))))$$

$$40731 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((0! + F(7))) + F((F(3!) + 1))))$$

$$40733 := ((407 + 3!) + (F(3)!))!$$

$$40734 := ((4! + F(((0! + F(7)) + 3!))) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$40735 := ((F((F(4))!))! - ((0! - (F(7) \times (F(3)^5))))))$$

$$40736 := (((4 \times F(07)) \times F(3!)) + (F(6))!)$$

$$40737 := (((4! - 0!) + 7!) \times F(3!)) + F(F(7))$$

$$40738 := (((-4!) + F(F(07))) \times F(3)) + 8!$$

$$40739 := (((F((F(4))!) + (F((0! + F(7)))) + (F(3)!))! + F(9))$$

$$40740 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((0! + (7))) \times (F(F((F(4))!) - 0!))))$$

$$40742 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + (7!/4!)) \times 2))$$

- 40743 := $(F(4!) - (((0! + 74)^{F(3)}))$
40744 := $((F(4!) + ((-0!) - F(F(7))) \times 4!) - F((F(4)!))$
40746 := $(F(4!) - (((-0!) - F(F(7))) \times (-4!)) + 6)$
40747 := $((((4! + 0!) \times F(F(7))) - 4) \times 7)$
40748 := $(((((4 + 0!)! - F(7)) \times 4) + 8!)$
40749 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (F(07) \times (4! + 9)))$
40752 := $(F(4!) - ((0! + F(F(7))) \times ((5 - F(2))!))$
40753 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (0! + (F((7 + 5) \times 3)))$
40755 := $(((((F(4)!)! + F((0! + (7)))) \times 55)$
40756 := $((F(F((F(4)!)) \times F((0! + (7)))) - (5 - (F(6)!))$
40760 := $((F((F(4)!))! + ((F((0! + (7))) \times F(F(6))) - 0!))$
40761 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (F((0! + (7))) \times F(F((6 \times 1))))$
40762 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (((0! + (7)))! + (F(F(6))^2)))$
40763 := $((F(F(4)) + ((0! + (7)))! + (F(F(6))^{F(3)}))$
40764 := $((F(F(4)) \times (0! + F(F(7)))) + ((F(6)! - (4!)))$
40765 := $(((((4! + 0!) \times F(7)) + (F(6)!)) + 5!)$
40766 := $((((F(4)!)! + (-0!) - ((F(7) \times F(F(6))) - (F(6)!)))$
40767 := $((((F(4)!)! + (((0! + (7)))! - (F(F(6)) \times F(7))))$
40768 := $((4 \times (0! + F(7))) \times (6! + 8))$
40769 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (F((0! + F(7))) - (F(6) \times (-9))))$
40772 := $((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F(07)) - 7) \times 2))$
40773 := $(((((4! + 0!) \times 7) \times F(F(7))) - F(3))$
40774 := $((((-F(4)) + F((0! + F(7)))) \times F(F(7))) - F(4!))$
40775 := $((((-4) - 0!) \times F(F(7))) \times (-7 \times 5))$
40776 := $((-((4! \times ((0! - F(7)) - (7)))) + (F(6)!))$
40778 := $((F((F(4)!)) \times (-0!)) + (((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) + 8!)))$
40782 := $((F(F(4)) \times (-0! + F(F(7)))) + ((8! - 2))$
40783 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(07))) + ((8! - 3))$
40784 := $((((F(F(4)) \times F(F(07))) + 8!) - F(F(4)))$
40785 := $((F((F(4)!))! + ((-0! + F(F(7))) + (F((8 + 5))))$
40786 := $((F(F(4)) \times (F(F(07)) + 8!)) - (F(6)!))$
40787 := $(((((4 \times 0!)! + F(F(7))) + 8!) + F(F(7)))$
40788 := $((((F(4)! \times 078) + 8!))$
40793 := $((-((F(4) - ((0! + F(7)) \times F(9)))) + (F(3)!))$
40794 := $((F(((F(4)! + (0! + F(7)))) + F(9)) \times (F(4)!))$

- 40796 := (((((4 × 0))! + F(7)) × F(9)) + (F(6))!)
40798 := (F(F(4)) + (((0! + F(7)) × F(9)) + 8!))
40803 := (((4! - 0!) × F(8)) + (F((03)!))!)
40804 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! - (F(8) × (0! - 4!))))
40804 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! - (F(8) × (0! - 4!))))
40806 := (((F(4))! × (0! + (80))) + (F(6))!)
40807 := (((F(4))! - ((0 - 8!) + F(F(07))))
40808 := (((((F(4))! + 0!) - F(F((8 - 0!)))) + 8!)
40810 := (((((F(4))! + (0! + F(8))) × F(10))
40817 := (((((4 + 0!))! + 8!) + F((1 + F(7))))
40823 := (((F(4))! × F(-(0! - F(8)))) + F(F((F(2) + 3!))))
40824 := ((4! × F(08)) + ((2 × 4)!)
40825 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! + (F(8) × (-((F(2) - (5))))!)))
40826 := (((((4! - 0!))! / (F(8))!) + ((2 + 6)!))
40828 := (4! + (((0! + F(8))²) + 8!))
40830 := ((F((F(4))!))! - (((0! - (8³)) + 0!))
40831 := (((F(F(4))^{0!+8}) + (F(3!))!) - 1)
40832 := ((F(F(4))^{0!+8}) + (F((3 × 2))!))
40833 := (((((4 × 0))! + 8!) + (F(3!)³))
40834 := (((F(4) - 0!) + 8!) + (F(3!)^{F(4)}))
40836 := ((4 + (08³)) + (F(6))!)
40837 := (((4! × F(08)) + (F(3!))!) + F(7))
40838 := ((F(4))! - ((0 - (8³)) - 8!))
40839 := ((F(4))! + (((0! + 8!) + (F(3)⁹))))
40840 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F(-(0! - 8)) × 40))
40842 := ((F(4))! × (F(-(0! - F(8)))) + 42))
40843 := (((((4! + 0!) × F(8)) - F(F(4))) + (F(3!))!)
40844 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((0! + F(8)) × 4!) - (4)))
40845 := (((4! + 0!) × F(8)) + ((F(4) + (5))!))
40846 := (((4! × (0! + F(8))) - F(F(4))) + (F(6))!)
40847 := (((F(4))! - ((0! + (8 × (4! - 7!))))
40848 := (((((4 × 0))! + F(8)) × 4!) + 8!)
40853 := (((4! × (0! + F(8))) + (5)) + (F(3!))!)
40855 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(-(0! - 8)) - 5!) × (-5)))
40860 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + 8) × 60))

- 40864 := $(-(40) - ((F(F(8)) - (6!)) \times (-4)))$
40865 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (-0!) + (F(8) \times (F(F(6)) + (5)))))$
40866 := $((((4 + 0!) + F(8)) \times F(F(6))) + (F(6)!))$
40867 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (0! + ((F(8) + F(F(6))) \times F(7)))))$
40868 := $(4 \times ((-0!) + F(F(8))) - ((6! + 8)))$
40869 := $(F(4!) - ((0! + F((F(8) - (6)))) \times 9))$
40872 := $((4!)/((0! + F(8)))! + ((7 + F(2)))!)$
40873 := $((F(4)! + (0! - ((F(8) - 7!) \times F(3!)))))$
40876 := $(4 \times (F(F(08)) + (-7) - 6!))$
40878 := $(F(4!) - (((0! + 8) \times F((7 + 8)))))$
40880 := $((F((F(4)!))! + ((0! - 8) \times (-80)))$
40882 := $((F(4!) - F(-((0! - 8)))) + (F(F(8))/(-2)))$
40884 := $(F(4!) - (((0! + F(8)) + F(F(8)))/F(F(4))))$
40886 := $((F((F(4)!))! - ((0! - (F(8) \times (F(8) + (6))))))$
40887 := $(F(4!) + (((0 - F(8)) \times F(8)) - 7!))$
40893 := $-((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (-0!) + ((8 \times 9) \times (3!))))$
40894 := $((F(4!) - 0!) - (F(F(8))/F((9/F(4))))$
40895 := $(F(4!) - (F(F(08))/F(F((9 - 5))))$
40896 := $((4!^{0! - 8 + 9}) + (F(6)!))$
40897 := $((F(4) - F(F(08))) - (9!/(-7)))$
40898 := $(((-4) + F(08)) \times F(9) + 8!)$
40899 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (0! + ((8 + 9) \times F(9))))$
40904 := $(((((F(4)! \times (-0!)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))) \times 4)$
40904 := $(((((F(4)! \times (-0!)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))) \times 4)$
40920 := $((F(4)! \times (F((0! + 9)) + F(20)))$
40925 := $((F((F(4)!))! + ((F((0! + 9))^2)/5))$
40926 := $((4! - 0!) + F(9)) \times (-2) + 6!)$
40927 := $((-F(4) + (-((0! - 9)))! + F((2 + F(7))))$
40928 := $(F((4! - 09)) - (2 - 8!))$
40929 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (F(-((0! - 9))) \times 29))$

40930 := $F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 0$
40931 := $F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 1$
40932 := $F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 2$
40933 := $F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 3$

$$40934 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 4$$

$$40935 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 5$$

$$40936 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 6$$

$$40937 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 7$$

$$40938 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 8$$

$$40939 := F(4! - 09) + F(3!)! + 9$$

$$40943 := (((F(4))! + 0!) \times F((9 + F(F(4)))) + (F(3))!)$$

$$40944 := (((F(4))!)! + (-((0! - 9)))! - (4! \times 4))$$

$$40945 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! + ((9! / ((F(4))!)! + 5!)))$$

$$40946 := (((F(4))!)! + ((0 - 94) + (F(6))!))$$

$$40947 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (-((0! - F(9))) \times ((F(4))! + F(7))))$$

$$40953 := (((F(4))!)! - ((0! - F(9)) + 5!)) + (F(3))!$$

$$40954 := ((4! + (-((0! - 9)))! + F((5 \times F(4))))$$

$$40955 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + F(9)) - (5! \times (-5))))$$

$$40958 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) + 0!) \times (F(9) - (5))) + 8!)$$

$$40963 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (-((0! - F(9))) + F((F(F(6)) - 3!))))$$

$$40964 := (4 + ((0! + 9) \times (F(6)^4)))$$

$$40966 := (((-(40) - F(9)) + 6!) + (F(6))!)$$

$$40967 := (-F(4!)) + ((-((0! - 9)) \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$40968 := ((4! \times ((0! + F(9)) - F(6))) + 8!)$$

$$40969 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (0! + ((-9) \times F(6)) \times (-9)))$$

$$40970 := (((F(4))!)! + (-((0! - 9)))! - (70))$$

$$40974 := ((4! + (-((0! - 9)))! + (7! / F((F(4))!)))$$

$$40975 := (((F(4))!)! + (-((0! - 9)))! - (F(7) \times 5))$$

$$40976 := (((F(4))!)! - ((0! - 9) \times (7! - F(6))))$$

$$40978 := (((F(4))!)! + ((0! - ((9 \times 7))) + 8!))$$

$$40980 := ((F((F(4))!))! - (((0! - F(9)) \times (F(8) - 0!))))$$

$$40983 := (-(((4! - 0!) + F(9)) - 8!)) + 3!!$$

$$40985 := (((F(4))!)! - F((0! + 9))) + (F(((8 - 5))!))!$$

$$40986 := (((F(4))! \times (0 - 9)) + ((8! + 6!)))$$

$$40987 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!) \times F(9)) + ((8! - F(7))))$$

$$40992 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F(-((0! - 9))) \times (F(9) - 2)))$$

$$40994 := ((F((F(4))!))! - ((F((0! + 9)) - (9^{F(4)}))))$$

$$40995 := (((F(4))!)! + (-((0! - 9)))! - (9 \times 5))$$

$$40996 := (((F(4))!)! + (-(((0! + F(9)) + 9)) + (F(6))!))$$

$$40998 := (((F(4))!)! + (((0! - 9) - F(9)) + 8!))$$

$$41006 := (((F(4))!)! - ((F((10 - 0!)) - (F(6))!))$$

$$41016 := ((-4!) + (((1 + 0!) + 1))!) + (F(6))!$$

$$41027 := (((F(4))!)! + (((10 - 2))! - F(7)))$$

$$41028 := (((F(4))!)! - ((10 + 2) - 8!))$$

$$41030 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 0$$

$$41031 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 1$$

$$41032 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 2$$

$$41033 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 3$$

$$41034 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 4$$

$$41035 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 5$$

$$41036 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 6$$

$$41037 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 7$$

$$41038 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 8$$

$$41039 := F(4)!! - 10 + F(3)! + 9$$

$$41040 := (((F(4))!)! \times ((F(10) + F(4)) - 0!))$$

$$41041 := (((F(4))!)! + (((F((10 - 4)))! + 1)))$$

$$41042 := (((F(4))!)! - ((-1 - 0!) - ((4 \times 2))!))$$

$$41043 := ((F(4) + (F((10 - 4)))!) + 3!!)$$

$$41044 := (((F(4))!)! + ((F((10 - 4)))! + 4))$$

$$41045 := (((F(4))!)! + (((F((10 - 4)))! + (5))))$$

$$41046 := (((F(4))! + ((10 - 4))!) + (F(6))!)$$

$$41047 := (((F(4))!)! + ((F((10 - 4)))! + 7))$$

$$41048 := (((F(4))!)! + (F((10 - 4)) + 8!))$$

$$41049 := (((F(4))!)! + (((F((10 - 4)))! + 9)))$$

$$41050 := (((F(4))!)! + 10) + (F((5 + 0!))!)$$

$$41053 := (((F(4))!)! + F(((1 + 0!) + (5)))) + (F(3))!$$

$$41063 := (((4! - 1) + (F(06))!) + 3!!)$$

$$41064 := ((4 + F(10)) \times (6! - 4!))$$

$$41066 := (((4! + 1) + 0!) + 6!) + (F(6))!$$

$$41068 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) + 1) \times F((0! + F(6)))) + 8!)$$

$$41069 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (1 + ((0! + F(F(6))) \times F(9))))$$

- 41072 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((1 - F((0! + F(7)))) × (-2)))
- 41073 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-1 + (F((0! + F(7))) × F(3))))
- 41074 := ((F(((4 - 1)!))! + (F((0! + F(7))) × F(F(4))))
- 41076 := ((F(F(4)) × (1 + F((0! + F(7)))) + (F(6))!)
- 41088 := ((F(4) × ((1 + 0!)⁸) + 8!)
- 41089 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(10) + (F(8) × F(9))))
- 41094 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-1 + F((0! + 9))) + ((F(4)!)!))
- 41095 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(10) + ((F((9 - 5))!))!))
- 41096 := (((F(4)!)! - ((-1 - F((0! + 9))) - (F(6))!))
- 41118 := (F(F((F(4)!)) × (F(11) × (1 + F(8))))
- 41124 := ((F(4))! × (F(11) + F((-F(2)) + F(F((F(4)!))))))
- 41128 := (((F(4)!)! + (((F(11) - F(2)) + 8!)))
- 41129 := (((F(4)!)! + (F(11))) + (-((F(2) - 9))!))
- 41130 := (((((F(4)!)! + (F(11))) + (F(3)!))! + 0!)
- 41133 := (((4 + F(11)) + 3!!) + (F(3)!))
- 41136 := ((4! × F((11 - F(3)))) + (F(6))!)
- 41139 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(11) + F(3)) × 9))
- 41153 := (((F(4))! + 1) × (-1 + 5!) + (F(3)!))
- 41156 := ((4 × (F(11) + 5!)) + (F(6))!)
- 41158 := (((F(4)!)! - (((1 + 1) - 5!) - 8!))
- 41167 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((1 + (-((1 - 6))!)) × 7))
- 41174 := (F(F(F((F(4)!))) - (((1 + 1) - 7!) × (F(4)!))
- 41178 := (((F(4))! × (11 × F(7))) + 8!)
- 41179 := -((F((F((F(4)!)) + 11)) + (7! × (-9))))
- 41184 := ((F((4!/(1 + 1))) + 8!) + ((F(4)!)!)
- 41186 := (((F(4))! × (-(((1 × 1) - 8))!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 41193 := (((F((F(4)!)) + (F(11))) × 9) + (F(3)!))
- 41208 := -((F(4!) + (F(((1 + 2)!)) × (-0! - F(F(8))))))
- 41216 := ((F(4!) × F(((1 + 2)!)))/(1 + F(6)))
- 41238 := (F(4!) - (((F(((1 + 2)!))! + ((3)!)))/8))
- 41244 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (F(F(((1 + 2)!)) × (-44)))
- 41247 := (F(4!) + (-(((1 + 2)⁴) - 7!))
- 41248 := -((F(4!) - (F(((1 + 2)!)) × ((F(4)! + F(F(8))))))
- 41256 := (-4!) + ((F(((1 + 2)!)) × 5!) + (F(6)!))
- 41263 := ((41 × (2 + F(F(6)))) + (F(3)!))

- 41264 := $(-(F(4!)) + ((F(((1 + 2)!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F((F(4)!)))$
- 41266 := $((-41) + F((2 \times F(6)))) + (F(6)!)$
- 41267 := $-((((F(4)! - ((1 + 2)!)) - (F(6)! - F(F(7))))$
- 41272 := $((((F(4)! + (F(((1 + 2)!)) + (F(F(7)) - F(2))))$
- 41273 := $(((((4 \times 1) \times 2))! + F(F(7))) + 3!)$
- 41274 := $((F(((4 - 1)!))! + (F(2) + F(F(7)))) + ((F(4)!))!$
- 41276 := $((F(4) + (((1 + 2)!))! + F(F(7))) + (F(6)!)$
- 41280 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (12 \times 80))$
- 41283 := $((-4!) + (F(((1 + 2)!))! + (F((8 \times F(3))))$
- 41284 := $((-(((4! + 1)^2)) + F(F(8))) \times 4)$
- 41286 := $((((4! - 1) \times 2) \times F(8)) + (F(6)!)$
- 41287 := $(F(4!) + (1 - ((2 \times F(8)) + 7!))$
- 41288 := $(((((4 + 1)! + F(2)) \times 8) + 8!)$
- 41292 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (12 \times (9^2)))$
- 41294 := $(-((((4 + 1) + 2)! + F(9))) + F(4!))$
- 41297 := $(F(4!) + (((1 + 2) - F(9)) - 7!))$
- 41298 := $((F((4 + 12)) - 9) + 8!)$
- 41304 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - (04)!)$
- 41306 := $((F(4!) - 1) - ((3! + 0!)! - F(F(6)))$
- 41307 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - F((0! + (7))))$
- 41308 := $((F((4 \times (1 + 3))) + 0!) + 8!)$
- 41314 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - 14)$
- 41314 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - 14)$
- 41316 := $((F((F(4)!))! + 1) + (F(3)!))! + (F(16)))$
- 41319 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - (1 \times 9))$
- 41320 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - F(((2 + 0)!))!$
- 41322 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - (F((2 + 2)))!)$
- 41323 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3)!))! - (2 + 3))$
- 41324 := $(F(4!) - (((1 + (3 \times 2)))! + (4)))$
- 41325 := $(F(4!) + (-((1 \times 3)) - ((2 + 5)!))$
- 41326 := $((F(4!) - F((1 \times 3))) - ((F(2) + (6)))!)$
- 41327 := $(F(4!) + (-1 - (((3 - 2) \times 7)!))$
- 41328 := $(F(4!) + (((1 + 3) \times 2)! / (-8))$
- 41329 := $((F(4!) + 1) - (((-3) + F(2)) + 9)!)$

$$41330 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 0$$

$$41331 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 1$$

$$41332 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 2$$

$$41333 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 3$$

$$41334 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 4$$

$$41335 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 5$$

$$41336 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 6$$

$$41337 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 7$$

$$41338 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 8$$

$$41339 := F(4!) - (1 + 3!)! + F(3) + 9$$

$$41341 := ((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!)) + F(((F(4))! + 1)))$$

$$41342 := (F(4!) - ((1 + 3!) \times (((F(4))!)! - 2)))$$

$$41343 := (((4^{-1+3!}) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(3!)!))$$

$$41345 := ((F(((4 - 1)!)!)) + (F(F(3)) + (4^5)))$$

$$41346 := ((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!)) + (4! - (6)))$$

$$41347 := (F(4!) + (((1 - 3!) + 4!) - 7!))$$

$$41348 := (((4! + F(13)) \times 4) + 8!)$$

$$41349 := ((F(((4 - 1)!)!)) + (F(F(3!)) \times 49))$$

$$41352 := (F(4!) + (((1 + 3)!)! - ((5 + 2)!)!))$$

$$41353 := ((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!)) + (5^{F(3)}))$$

$$41354 := -((((((F(4))! + 1)!)! - F(F(3!))) + (-5 - F(4!)))$$

$$41355 := ((F((F(4))!)!)) + ((1 + F(3!)) \times (5! - (5)))$$

$$41356 := ((F((F((F(4))!) + 1))^{F(3)} - (5! - (F(6))!))$$

$$41357 := (F(4!) + (((1 + 3)!)! + (5)) - 7!))$$

$$41358 := ((F(4))! \times (F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + (5! + 8)))$$

$$41359 := ((-41) + (F(3!)!)) + (5! \times 9))$$

$$41362 := ((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!)) + F((F(6) + F(2))))$$

$$41364 := ((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!)) + (6^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$41368 := ((41 \times F(3!)) + ((6! + 8!)))$$

$$41373 := (((F(4)^{1+3}) \times F(7)) + (F(3!)!))$$

$$41374 := (((4! - 1) \times F(3)) - 7!) + F(4!))$$

$$41375 := ((F((F(4))!)!)) + (((-1 - F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) \times 5))$$

$$41376 := (((F(4))! \times (1 + F(F(3!)))) + (7!)) \times F(6))$$

- 41377** := $(F(4!) + (((1 + 3!) \times 7) - 7!))$
41383 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!)) + F((8 + F(3))))$
41384 := $(((-((4 + 1)!) + 3!) - F(F(8))) \times (-4))$
41394 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) + (((-1 + 3!)! \times 9) - (F(4)!)!))$
41395 := $((-((4 + 1)) + (F(3)!)!) + (9 \times 5!))$
41396 := $(-(4) + (((-1 + 3!)! \times 9) + (F(6)!)!))$
41397 := $(F(4!) + (1 + ((F(3) \times F(9)) - 7!)))$
41398 := $-((F(F(4)) - (((-1 + 3!)! \times 9) + 8!)))$
41409 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) + (((1 + 4)!) + 0!) \times 9))$
41416 := $((F(4)!)! - (-((F(14) - 1)) - (F(6)!)!))$
41417 := $((F(4)!)! + ((F(14) + ((1 + 7)!)!)))$
41418 := $((F(4)!)! + ((F(14) + 1) + 8!))$
41423 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) + (-1 + ((F(4!)/2)/F(F(3!))))))$
41424 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) + (((1 - 4!) \times (-2)) \times 4!))$
41432 := $(-((F(4!) + 1)) + (F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times F((F(F(3!)) - 2))))$
41433 := $((F(4) \times (F(14) - 3!)) + (F(3)!)!)$
41434 := $(-((F(4!) - 1)) + (F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4))))))$
41436 := $(((-F(F((F(4)!)!))) - F((-1 + F(F((F(4)!)!)))) \times (-3!)) + (6!))$
41438 := $(((((F(4)!)! + (F(14))) + F(F(3!))) + 8!))$
41439 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) - 1) + ((F((F(4)!)!)) / (F(3) + F(9))))$
41443 := $((F(4) \times F(14)) - F((F(4)!)!)) + (F(3)!)!$
41444 := $((F(F((F(4)!)!)) - F((-1 + F(F((F(4)!)!)))) / (-F(4)!)!)) + (F((F(4)!)!))!$
41445 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + (F(4)!)!)!)) - ((F(4) - 5!)))$
41447 := $(((((4 + 1)!) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(4!) - (7!))))$
41449 := $(F(F(((F(4)!) + 1))) + ((F(4!) - (F(4!)/9))))$
41451 := $((F(4) \times F(14)) + (F((5 + 1)!)!))$
41453 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + (F(4)!)!)!)) + (5^3))$
41454 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + (F(4)!)!)!)) + (5! + (F(4)!)!))$
41456 := $((F(4) \times F(14)) + (5)) + (F(6)!)!$
41457 := $(F((F(4)!)!)) + ((1 + F(4!)) + (5! - 7!))$
41464 := $(F((F(4)!)!)) \times (-1 - (4 \times (6^4)))$
41466 := $((4!^{1 \times 4}) / F(6)) - (6)$
41467 := $(F(4!) + (F(14) \times (-6 + 7)))$
41468 := $(((((F(4!) - 1) \times F(F(4))) - (F(6)!)!)) - F(F(8)))$
41469 := $(F(4) \times (-1 + (4!^{-6+9})))$

- 41471 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-1 + (F((F(4)!)) × F((F(7) - 1))))))
 41473 := (F(4!) - (((F(14) × F(7)) - 3!)))
 41474 := (F(F(F(4))) - ((-F(14)) × F(F(7))) + F(4!))
 41475 := ((F(((4 - 1)!))! + ((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) × (-5)))
 41476 := ((F(4!) + (1⁴)) - (F(F(7)) × F(F(6))))
 41477 := ((F(((4 - 1)!))! + (F((4 + 7)) × F(7)))
 41478 := ((F(4!) + F((1 × 4))) + (F(F(7)) × (-F(8))))
 41479 := -((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (((1 + 4!) × F(F(7))) × 9)))
 41482 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((1 + ((F(4)!))! + ((F(8)²))))
 41483 := (F(4!) - ((F(F((1 + (F(4)!))) × F(8)) - F(3!)))
 41484 := ((F((F((F(4)! + 1))^{F(F(4))}) - (-8! - F((F(4)!))))
 41485 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((1 + 4) × F((8 + 5))))
 41487 := ((F(4!) - 1) - (F((F(4)!)) × F((8 + 7))))
 41488 := (F(4!) - (F(((-1 + 4!) - 8)) × 8))
 41489 := (-((F(4!) - 1) + (F(-((F(4) - F(8)))) × F(9)))
 41490 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((1 + (F(4)!)) × 90))
 41496 := (4! × (1 - ((4! × (-9)) × F(6))))
 41499 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-1 + 4!) + (F(9) × F(9))))
 41510 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((1 - 5!) × 10))
 41519 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-1 + (5! × (1 + 9))))
 41524 := (((F((F(4)!)) - (F(15))) × (-2)) + (F((F(4)!))!))
 41525 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((1 - (5! × (-2))) × 5))
 41527 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(15) × 2) - F(7)))
 41528 := (((F(4)! - (F(15))) × (-2)) + 8!)
 41533 := ((F(F((F(4)!)) × ((-1 + 5!) × F(F(3!)))) - F(F(F(3!))))
 41534 := (((F(F(4)) × F(15)) + (F(3!)!) - (F(4)!))
 41535 := ((F(((4 - 1)!))! + ((5 × (3⁵))))
 41536 := (F(4!) - (((F(15) - 3!) × F(6))))
 41538 := ((F(F(4)) × F(15)) - (F(3) - 8!))
 41540 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(15) × (F(4) - 0!)))
 41541 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(15) × F(F(4))) + 1))
 41542 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((1 + F((5 × F(4)))) × 2))
 41543 := (((F(F(4)) × F(15)) + F(4)) + (F(3!)!))
 41544 := (((4!^{F(-1+5)}) + (4!)) × F(4))

- 41545 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(15) × F(F(4))) + (5)))
- 41546 := ((F(F(4)) × (F(15) + F(4))) + (F(6))!)
- 41547 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(15) × F(F(4))) + 7))
- 41548 := ((F(F(4)) × (F(15) + (4))) + 8!)
- 41549 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(15) × F(F(4))) + 9))
- 41553 := ((F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 1))/5) - (5! - (F(3!)!))
- 41559 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(F((1 + 5))) × 59))
- 41564 := (((F(F(4)) × F(15)) + (F(6))! + (4!))
- 41568 := (F(4!) + (((-1) × 5!) + 6!) × (-8))
- 41569 := (F(4!) + (1 - (5! × (6 + F(9))))
- 41574 := -((((F(4)! - (F((1 + 5)))! - (7!/4)))
- 41576 := ((F((F(4)!)) × 157) + (F(6))!)
- 41577 := (- (F(4!) - (F((-1 + F((-5) + F(7)))))) × (-F(7)))
- 41582 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(15) + F(8)) × 2))
- 41584 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (158 × F((F(4)!)))
- 41589 := ((F(((4 - 1)!))! - ((5! + F(8)) × (-9)))
- 41592 := -((4! - ((1 + 5) × F(9))²))
- 41598 := (((F(F((F(4)!)) - (-1 - 5!)) × 9) + 8!)
- 41615 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-1 + (6⁻¹⁺⁵)))
- 41623 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (1 + (62 × F(F(3!))))
- 41624 := (((F(4)! × F((1 + F(6))))² + F((F(4)!))
- 41636 := (((-4) × F(16))/(-3) + (F(6))!)
- 41637 := (F(F(((4 - 1)!)) + ((6^{3!}) - 7!))
- 41639 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-1 - (((6 × F(3))!)/(-9!))))
- 41643 := ((F(((4 - 1)!))! + ((F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}) × 3))
- 41644 := ((4! + F((1 + F(6)))) × (((F(4)! - F(F(4)))
- 41646 := ((F(4) × (1 + (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))}))) + (F(6))!)
- 41647 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((1 + F(F(6)))) - (4⁷)))
- 41649 := (((F(4)! - 1) + ((-1 + (F(6))! + F((4! - 9))))
- 41653 := (F((4! - 1) + ((-6) + 5!)^{F(3)}))
- 41663 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-1 - (F(F(6)) × (-F(6)^{F(3)}))))
- 41664 := (((F(4)! + 1) × (F(6) × (6! + 4!)))
- 41665 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (1 - ((F(6)!)/(-6 × 5))))
- 41666 := (((F((F(4)!))! × (-16))/(-F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6))))

- 41672 := $(F((F(4))!) \times (((1 + 6))! + (F(7)^2)))$
- 41673 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (1 + (F(6) \times (F(7)^{F(3)}))))$
- 41676 := $((F(4))! \times (F(F((1 + 6))) - 7) + (F(6))!)$
- 41677 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (1 + (6 \times (F(F(7)) - 7))))$
- 41684 := $((((4! + 1) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(8))) \times (-4))$
- 41685 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((F((1 + 6)) \times F(8)) \times 5))$
- 41688 := $(((-F(F(4))) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))))/8 + 8!)$
- 41692 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! - ((6! - F(9)) \times (-2)))$
- 41693 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (1 + ((6! - F(9)) \times F(3))))$
- 41694 := $-((F((F(4))!) - ((-1 + 6!) \times (F(9) + 4!))))$
- 41697 := $-((((((4 - 1))!))! - (F(6))! - (9 \times F(F(7))))))$
- 41706 := $((F(4))! \times ((-1 + F(F(7))) - 0!) + (F(6))!)$
- 41708 := $(F(4!) + ((-1) \times F(F(7))) \times (-0! - F(8)))$
- 41712 := $((F(4))! \times (-1 + F(F(7)))) + (F(((1 + 2))!))!$
- 41713 := $((F(4))! \times (-1 + F(F(7)))) + 1 + (F(3!))!$
- 41717 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (-1 - (F(F(7)) \times (1 - 7))))$
- 41718 := $((F(4))! \times F(F((1 \times 7)))) + ((1 \times 8))!$
- 41723 := $((F(4))! \times (1 + F(F(7)))) - F(2) + (F(3!))!$
- 41724 := $((F(4))! \times (1 + F(F(7)))) + ((2 \times 4))!$
- 41726 := $((F(4))! \times (1 + F(F(7)))) + (2 + (F(6))!)$
- 41728 := $(F(4!) - ((1 - F(F(7))) \times (F(2) - F(8))))$
- 41732 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (((-1 - F(7)) + 3!!) \times 2))$
- 41733 := $((F(4))! \times (-1 + F(F(7)))) + F(F(3!)) + (F(3!))!$
- 41734 := $(F(4!) - ((F(17) + 3!!) \times F(F(4))))$
- 41737 := $((F(4))! \times (1 + F(F(7)))) + (F(3!))! + F(7)$
- 41738 := $((F(4))! + (-1 + ((F(F(7)) \times 3) + 8!)))$
- 41743 := $((4! + 1) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(4))!)) + (F(3!))!$
- 41744 := $(F(4!) - ((17 \times 4)^{F(F(4))}))$
- 41746 := $(((((4 - 1))!))! - 7) \times F(F(4)) + (F(6))!$
- 41747 := $((F(4))! \times ((1 - F(F(7)))/(-4))) - F(7)$
- 41748 := $((4 + 1) + F(F(7))) \times (F(4))! + 8!$
- 41749 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (1 + ((7 \times (F(4))!) \times F(9))))$
- 41754 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (((1 + F(F(7))) + 5) \times (F(4))!))$
- 41755 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (((-1 + F(7)) \times 5!) - 5!))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 41756 &:= ((-4) - ((1 - F(7)) \times 5!)) + (F(6)!) \\
 41758 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (((-1 + F(7)) \times 5!) + 8!))) \\
 \\
 41760 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 0 \\
 41761 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 1 \\
 41762 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 2 \\
 41763 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 3 \\
 41764 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 4 \\
 41765 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 5 \\
 41766 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 6 \\
 41767 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 7 \\
 41768 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 8 \\
 41769 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-1 + 7)! + F(6)! + 9 \\
 \\
 41773 &:= (((F(4))!)! + (((1 + 7)! + F(7)) + 3!)) \\
 41774 &:= ((F((F(4))!)! + (((-((1 - 7))! + 7) \times F(F(4)))))) \\
 41776 &:= (((-((4! + 1)) + F(F(7))) \times 7) + (F(6)!) \\
 41784 &:= (4! \times (F(17) + F((8 + 4)))) \\
 41794 &:= (((F(4))!)! + (((1 + 7)! + F(9)))) + ((F(4))!)! \\
 41805 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(18) + 0!)) \times 5) \\
 41815 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(18) - 1)) \times 5) \\
 41828 &:= ((4 \times F(-(((1 - 8) \times 2)))) + 8!) \\
 41833 &:= (F(4!) + (1 - (F(8) \times (3!^3)))) \\
 41836 &:= (4 \times ((F(F(-((1 - 8)))) - ((3!)!) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 41838 &:= (((((4! - 1))! / (F(8))!) \times 3) + 8!) \\
 41844 &:= (((((F(4))!)! + F((1 + 8))) \times (-F(4)!) + F(4!)) \\
 41849 &:= ((F((F(4))!)! + (-1 + ((F(8) + 4!) \times F(9)))) \\
 41854 &:= ((F((F(4))!)! + (F(-((1 - 8))) \times (5! - F(F(4)))))) \\
 41856 &:= (4! \times ((F(18) - 5!) - 6!)) \\
 41857 &:= -((((4! - 1) - 8!) - (5! \times F(7))) \\
 41864 &:= (((4! \times (1 - F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4) \\
 41868 &:= ((4 \times (1 + F(F(8)))) - ((F(6))! / F(8))) \\
 41874 &:= ((F(((4 - 1))!)! + (F(8) \times 74)) \\
 41875 &:= ((-((4 + 1)) + 8!) + (F(7) \times 5!)) \\
 41889 &:= (F(4!) + (((1 + 8) - 8!) / 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}41890 &:= (F(4!) + (1 + ((8!/(-9)) + 0!))) \\41892 &:= (-(((4! + 1) - 8!) + F((F(9)/2))) \\41893 &:= (F(4!) - (1 + ((8!/9) - 3!))) \\41894 &:= ((F(4))! + (F(18) + (F(9)^{F(4)}))) \\41895 &:= (F(F(((4 - 1))!)) \times (F(8) \times 95)) \\41896 &:= (F(4!) + (((1 \times 8)!/(-9)) + F(6))) \\41916 &:= (F((-4) + F(-(1 - 9)))) - (1 - (F(6))!) \\41917 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times ((-(1 - 9))! + F(17))) \\41918 &:= (F((-4) + F(-(1 - 9)))) + (1 + 8!) \\41923 &:= ((F(((4 - 1))!))! + (F((F(9)/2) + 3!)) \\41924 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((1 + F((F(9)/2))) + (F(4))!)) \\41926 &:= (F((F(4))!) + ((1 + F((F(9)/2))) + (F(6))!)) \\41928 &:= ((4! \times (-1 - (F(9) \times (-2)))) + 8!) \\41934 &:= (F(4!) - ((19 + 3!!) \times (F(4))!)) \\41936 &:= (((F(4!)/(1 \times 9)) \times F(3!)) + (6!)) \\41937 &:= (((F(4!) - 1) + F((9 + 3!))) - (7!)) \\41938 &:= ((F(((4 - 1))!))! + (F((F(9)/F(3))) + (F(8)))) \\41940 &:= (((F(F((F(4))!)) - 1) \times 9) \times F(F(((F(4))! + 0!))) \\41941 &:= (F(4!) - (19 \times F(F(((F(4))! + 1)))) \\41944 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((-1 + (F(9) \times (F(4))!)) \times F((F(4))!))) \\41946 &:= -(((F(4))! - ((19 \times F(4!))/F(F(6)))) \\41947 &:= (((41 \times F(9)) + (F((F(4))!))! + F(F(7))) \\41948 &:= (-4) + ((19 \times F(4!))/F(8)) \\41949 &:= ((4 + F((1 + 9))) \times (((F(4))! - 9)) \\41952 &:= ((F(4!) \times 19)/F(F(((5 - 2))!))) \\41954 &:= ((F(4!) - (F(19))) - F(F((5 + F(F(4))))) \\41974 &:= -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((F(-(1 - 9))) \times 7!)/F(F(4)))) \\41976 &:= (((4! - 1) \times 9) + 7!) \times F(6) \\41978 &:= (F(((4 - 1) \times 9)) + ((F(7))!/(-8!))) \\41979 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F(-(1 - 9))) \times 79) \\41998 &:= (F(4!) - (F(19) + (9 \times F(8)))) \\42000 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) \times 2000) \\42036 &:= (F(4!) + (((2 + 0))! \times (-F(3) + 6!))) \\42037 &:= -((((F((F(4))!)) - F(20)) - (F(3))!) + (7!)) \\42039 &:= (F(4!) - (((2 + 0))! \times (3!) + 9))\end{aligned}$$

- 42042 := $(F(4!) + (-((2 + 0!)!) \times (((F(4))!)! + F(2))))$
- 42043 := $((F(4!) + F(2)) - (0! + ((F(4))!)! \times 3!))$
- 42044 := $((((F(4))!)! \times -((2 + 0!)!)) - (4 - F(4!)))$
- 42045 := $((F((F(4))!)! + (F(20) - ((F(F(4)) + (5)))!))$
- 42046 := $(F(4!) + (-2) \times (0! + (F(4) \times 6!)))$
- 42047 := $((((4 + 2))! - 0!) + F(4!)) - (7!))$
- 42048 := $(((4!/2)^{F(04)} + 8!))$
- 42052 := $((((F((F(4))!)!)/2 - (F(F(F((0! + (5)))))) \times (-2)))$
- 42054 := $(F(4!) + ((F(2) - (0! + (5)))! \times (F(4))!))$
- 42066 := $(F(4!) + (((-2) - 0!) + 6!) \times (-6))$
- 42079 := $((F((F(4))!)! + ((F(20) - 7!) + F(9)))$
- 42084 := $((F((F(4))!)! + ((2 \times F(08))^{F(F(4))}))$
- 42143 := $((((F((F(4))!) - F(21))/(-F(4))!) + (F(3))!))$
- 42144 := $((F((F(4))!)! + ((F(21) - F(F(4)))/(F(4))!))$
- 42147 := $(F(4!) - (((21^{F(4)}) - 7!))$
- 42153 := $((F(4) \times (F(2) + F(15))) + (F(3))!)$
- 42156 := $((F(4) \times (2 + F(15))) + (F(6))!)$
- 42166 := $((F(4!) - F((-2) + F(F((1 \times 6)))))) - (F(F(6)))$
- 42168 := $((F((F(4))!) \times (-2) + F(F((1 + 6)))) + 8!)$
- 42174 := $((((F(4) - (21)) \times F(F(7))) + F(4!))$
- 42176 := $(((4 \times 2))! - ((1 - F(F(7))) \times F(6)))$
- 42177 := $((F((F(4))!)! + ((F(((2 + 1))!) \times F(F(7))) - 7))$
- 42178 := $-(((F(4))! - ((F(((2 + 1))!) \times F(F(7))) + 8!))$
- 42183 := $-((((F(4))!)! + ((F(2) - F(18)))) - (F(3))!))$
- 42184 := $((F(4!) - F((F(2) + (18)))) - F(4))$
- 42185 := $-(((F(4!) + 2) - (F((1 + F(8))) \times 5)))$
- 42186 := $((F(4!) - F(2)) - F((F(-((1 - 8))) + 6)))$
- 42187 := $(F(4!) - F((-2) + F(((1^8) + 7))))$
- 42188 := $((((F(4!) + F(2)) + F((-1 + F(8)))) - F(F(8)))$
- 42189 := $((F((F(4))!)! + (21 \times 89))$
- 42190 := $(F(4!) - ((-2) + F(19)) - 0!))$
- 42193 := $(F(4!) - ((F(2) \times F(19)) - 3!))$
- 42194 := $(F(4!) + (F(21) - (9!/4!)))$
- 42196 := $(F(4!) + ((F(2) - F(19)) + F(6)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42208 &:= ((F(4!) - F(-(F(2) - (20)))) + (F(8))) \\
 42234 &:= (((F((F(4)!))!)/F(F((F((2+2))!))) + (((F(3)! - (F(4)!))) \\
 42235 &:= (((F((F(4)!))!)/F(F((F((2+2))!))) + (((F(3)! - (5)))) \\
 42236 &:= (-4) - ((-22) \times (F(3)!)/F(F(6))) \\
 42237 &:= (((F((F((F(4)! + 2) + 2)^{F(3)}) \times F(7)) \\
 42238 &:= (-F(F(4))) - ((-22) \times (F(3)!)/F(8))) \\
 \\
 42240 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 0 \\
 42241 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 1 \\
 42242 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 2 \\
 42243 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 3 \\
 42244 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 4 \\
 42245 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 5 \\
 42246 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 6 \\
 42247 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 7 \\
 42248 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 8 \\
 42249 &:= F(F(4)!)/F(F(F(2+2)!)) + F(F(4)! + 9 \\
 \\
 42252 &:= ((F(4!)/(2+2)! + (F((5-2)!))) \\
 42254 &:= ((F((F(4)^2)) \times (-F(2+5!)) + F(4!)) \\
 42256 &:= (((4^2) \times (F(2+5!)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 42264 &:= -(((4^{F(2+2)!}) + F(6)) - F(4!)) \\
 42266 &:= (F(4!) - (((2+2)^6) + 6)) \\
 42270 &:= (F(4!) - (2 + (2^{F(7)-0!})) \\
 42271 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(2) + (2^{F(7)-1}))) \\
 42272 &:= (F(4!) - (2^{2 \times 7 - 2})) \\
 42273 &:= (F(4!) - ((-2) + (2^{F(7)})/F(3))) \\
 42274 &:= (F(4!) - (-2) + ((F(2) + (7)^4)) \\
 42278 &:= (((4! - 2) \times F((-2) + F(7))) + 8!) \\
 42284 &:= ((4! - 2) \times (2 + (8!/F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 42286 &:= (((F((4^2)) \times 2) + 8!) - F(6)) \\
 42287 &:= (((F((4^2)) \times 2) + 8!) - (7)) \\
 42288 &:= -(((F(4)! - ((2 \times F((2 \times 8))) + 8!)) \\
 42294 &:= ((F((4^2)) \times 2) + (F((9 - F(4))))!) \\
 42323 &:= (((((F(4)! + (-2) \times F(F(F(3!)))))) \times (-2)) - (F(F(3!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}42328 &:= ((4! \times ((2 \times F(F(3!)))^2)) - 8) \\42329 &:= ((-((F(4!) - F(2))) + (F(3!))!) \times (2 - 9)) \\42332 &:= ((-(((F(4))!)!) + ((2 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - 3!)) \times 2) \\42333 &:= (((F(4!)/23) - 3) + (F(3!))!) \\42334 &:= (((((F(4))!)! - 2) + (F(3!))!) + ((3!^4))) \\42335 &:= ((F(4!) - F(2)) - ((F(3!))!/(F(3) \times 5))) \\42336 &:= (((4! \times F(2^3))^{F(3)})/6) \\42337 &:= (F((4! - F(2))) - ((3!)! \times (- (3! + F(7)))))) \\42338 &:= ((F(4!)/23) + (F(3) + 8!)) \\42342 &:= ((F(4))! \times (F(2) + ((F(F(3!)) \times 4^2))) \\42343 &:= ((-((F(4!) + F(2))) + (F(3!))!) \times (- (4 + 3))) \\42344 &:= ((F(F((4 \times 2))) - ((3!)!/F(F(4)))) \times 4) \\42346 &:= ((F(4!)/(-2)) - (3! - (4^{F(6)}))) \\42347 &:= (4 + (((-F(2)) + (F(3!))!) - F(4!)) \times (-7)) \\42348 &:= (((((4! + 2)^{F(3)}) \times F(4)) + 8!) \\42350 &:= (F((F((F(4))!) + 2)) \times ((3!)! + (50))) \\42352 &:= ((F(4!)/(-2)) + ((F(3!)^5) \times 2)) \\42354 &:= (((((F(4))!)!/2) + F(3)) \times (5! - F(4))) \\42357 &:= (-F(4) + (-(((2 + 3)!)! \times (- (5! - F(F(7)))))) \\42359 &:= (-F(4) + ((2 - 3!) \times (-59))) \\42360 &:= -((((F(4))!)! - ((2 - 3!) \times (-60)))) \\42362 &:= (((((F(4))!)! - 2) \times (- (3 - 62))) \\42363 &:= (((F(F((F(4))!)^2) \times 3) + ((F(6))! + 3!)) \\42364 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (2^{F(3!)})) + (((F(6))! - 4))) \\42365 &:= ((F((F(4))!)!) + (((-F(2) - 3!) + F(F(F(6))))/5)) \\42366 &:= -((((F(F(4)) - (2^{3+F(6)})) - (F(6))!) \\42372 &:= ((-(((F(4))!)!) - (- (2) \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 7))) \times 2) \\42373 &:= ((-F((4!/2))) + (F(3!))!) + (F(7)^3) \\42374 &:= (((-((F(4!) + 2)) + (F(3!))!) \times (-7)) + (4!)) \\42376 &:= (((4! + ((F(2) + 3!))!) + F(F(7))) \times F(6)) \\42384 &:= (F(4!) - ((- (2) - (F(3!) \times (-F(8)))) \times 4!)) \\42386 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((2 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(8) - 6!)))) \\42390 &:= ((F((F(4))!)!) + (23 \times 90)) \\42393 &:= (-4!) + ((F(F((F(2) + 3!))) \times 9) + (F(3!))!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42394 &:= (-(((F(4) - (2^{3!})) \times F(9))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 42396 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F((F(2) + 3!))) \times 9) - (F(F(6)))))) \\
 42397 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(2) - F(F(3!))) + (9 \times F(F(7)))))) \\
 42398 &:= ((F(4!) - F(2)) - (F(F(3!)) \times (9 \times F(8)))) \\
 42399 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) + (F(F(3!)) \times 99)) \\
 42407 &:= (F(4!) + (((-(2^4) - 0!) \times F(F(7)))))) \\
 42417 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) - ((F((F(4)!)) + 1) \times (-F(F(7)))))) \\
 42419 &:= (((F((F(4)!))! + 2) + (F(F((F(4)! + 1))) \times 9)) \\
 42424 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(2) - F((4^2))) \times (-4))) \\
 42433 &:= ((F((4^2)) \times 43) - F(3!)) \\
 42436 &:= (((42 + 4)^{F(3)}) + (F(6)!)) \\
 42437 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-F(2) + ((F(4)!))!) - (-3!) \times F(F(7)))))) \\
 42438 &:= (-(42) + ((F(4) \times (3!)!) + 8!)) \\
 42442 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-2) + (F((F(4)!))!)) / (F(F((F(4)!)) - 2))) \\
 42444 &:= (F(4!) - ((F((2^4)) \times 4) - 4!)) \\
 42446 &:= (-(F((F(4)^2))) - (((F(4)!))! \times (-F(4))) - (F(6)!)) \\
 42449 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (((F(2) + ((F(4)!))!) \times F(4)) - F(9))) \\
 42454 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (-2) + (4! \times F((5 + (F(4)!))))) \\
 42456 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) + (4! \times F((5 + 6)))) \\
 42458 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (2^{F(F(4)!)})) / 5) + 8!) \\
 42459 &:= (-(F((4 \times 2))) + (((F(4)!))! \times 59)) \\
 42462 &:= (((4! + F((2^4))) \times F(F(6))) \times 2) \\
 42463 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(2) + (F(4) \times (6! - 3!)))) \\
 42464 &:= (F(4!) + (((2^{F(F(4)!)} + (6!)) \times (-4))) \\
 42465 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) + (F(4) \times (6! - (5)))) \\
 42466 &:= (((((F(4)!))! - 2) \times F(4)) - (F(6) - (F(6)!)) \\
 42467 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) + ((F(4) \times 6!) - F(7))) \\
 42468 &:= ((4! / (-2)) + ((F(4) \times 6!) + 8!)) \\
 42469 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (-2) + ((F(4) \times 6!) - 9))) \\
 42473 &:= (((F(4) \times ((2 + 4)!) - (7)) + (F(3)!))! \\
 42474 &:= (((((F(4)!))! - 2) \times F(4)) + (F(((7 - 4)!))!)) \\
 42476 &:= (((((F(4)!))! + F(2)) \times F(4)) - (7 - (F(6)!)) \\
 42477 &:= (((((F(4)!))! - F(2)) \times F(4)) + (F((-7) + F(7))))! \\
 42478 &:= ((F(4!) / 2) + (((F(4)! \times 7!) - F(F(8))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$42479 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (-F(2)) - (((F(4)!)! \times (-F((F(7) - 9))))))$$

$$42480 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 0$$

$$42481 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 1$$

$$42482 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 2$$

$$42483 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 3$$

$$42484 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 4$$

$$42485 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 5$$

$$42486 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 6$$

$$42487 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 7$$

$$42488 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 8$$

$$42489 := (4 + 2)! \times F(4) + 8! + 9$$

$$42492 := ((F(4!)/(-2)) + ((F(4)! \times F(F((9 - F(2))))))$$

$$42493 := ((-F(4)) - ((2^{F(4)!}) \times (-F(9)))) + (F(3!))!$$

$$42494 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((2^{F(4)!}) \times F(9)) - F(F(4))))$$

$$42496 := (((4^2) \times 4) \times F(9)) + (F(6))!$$

$$42498 := (F(F(4)) - (((2^{F(4)!}) \times (-F(9))) - 8!))$$

$$42504 := ((F(4!)/(2 \times (-5) - 0!)) + F(4!))$$

$$42506 := (((F(4)^{2+5}) - 0!) + (F(6))!)$$

$$42507 := ((F(4)^{2+5}) + ((0! + (7)))!)$$

$$42508 := (((F(4)^{2+5}) + 0!) + 8!)$$

$$42509 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(2))/5) + ((-((0! - 9)))!))$$

$$42523 := (((F(F((F(4)!))^2) \times 5) - (2 - (F(3!))!))$$

$$42524 := (F(4!) - ((2 + (5!/2))^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$42525 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(F((F(2) + (5))))^2) \times 5))$$

$$42526 := ((F(4!)/F(F((F(2) + 5)))) - (2 - (F(6))!))$$

$$42528 := (F(4!) - ((-2) \times 5!) \times (-2 \times 8))$$

$$42529 := (F(4!) + ((F(2) - (5! \times (-2) + F(9))))))$$

$$42533 := (((F(F((F(4)!))^2) \times 5) + ((F(3!))! + F(3!)))$$

$$42534 := (((F(4!)/F(F((F(2) + 5)))) + (F(3!))!) + F(4)!)$$

$$42535 := ((F(4!) - F(F((2 + 5)))) - ((3!) \times 5))$$

$$42536 := ((F(4!)/F(F((F(2) + 5)))) + ((F(3!) + (F(6))!))$$

$$42537 := ((F(4!) + 2) + ((-5) \times (3!)! - F(F(7))))$$

$$42538 := (F(4!) - (2 \times (-5) + ((F(3!))!/F(8))))$$

- 42539 := (((F(4))!)! + F(2)) × ((5^{F(3)}) + F(9))
- 42543 := (((F(4))!)! + F(F((F(2) + 5)))) × F(4) + (F(3))!)
- 42544 := ((F((F(4))!) × (2 + (5! × (-4)))) + F(4!))
- 42545 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (25 × F((F(4))! + (5))))
- 42546 := (F(4) × ((-((F(2) - 5!))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(6))))
- 42562 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((-2) + 5!) × (F(F(6)) - 2))
- 42574 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((-2) + 5!) × F(7)) + ((F(4))!))
- 42584 := (-((4 + 2)!) + ((5! - F(F(8))) × (-4)))
- 42587 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) × 5!) + ((8! - F(7))))
- 42588 := (((4! / (-2)) + 5!) × F(8)) + 8!
- 42592 := (F(4!) - ((-2) + 5!) × (F(9) - 2))
- 42594 := (((F(4)²) - 5!) × F(9)) + F(4!)
- 42596 := (F(4!) - (2 - (-5) × (F(9) + 6!)))
- 42623 := (((F(4!) - 2) + (F(6))!) / 2) - (3!)!
- 42624 := (F(4!) + (F((2 × 6)) × (-2 - 4!)))
- 42624 := (F(4!) + (F((2 × 6)) × (-2 - 4!)))
- 42625 := (((F(4))!)! + F((2 + F(6)))) × F((2 × 5))
- 42626 := (((4! - 2) × 6!) × 2) + F(F(F(6)))
- 42628 := (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-((F((2 × 6))²)) - F(F(8))))
- 42634 := (-F(4!) - ((F((-2) + F(F(6)))) + (F(3))!) × (-F(F(4))))
- 42636 := (F(4)! × (((-2) × (F(6))!) / F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6))))
- 42637 := ((F(F(4))!)! + (F((-2 + F(F(6)))) - ((F(3!) × F(F(7))))))
- 42639 := (((F(4))!)! - (-2 - (F(6))!)) + F((F(3!) + 9))
- 42640 := (F(4!) - ((2 × F(6)) × F(F((F(4))! + 0!))))
- 42642 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (2 × (6! + (F(F((F(4))!)²))))
- 42647 := ((F(F(4))!)! - (((F(2) - (6! / 4)) × F(7))))
- 42653 := ((((((F(4))!)! - F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) / 5) + (F(3))!)
- 42656 := (4 × ((-2) × (F(F(6)) + 5!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 42660 := (((F(4)²) - 6!) × (-60))
- 42663 := (F(4!) - (-((F(2) - (6))) × (F(F(6)) + (3!)!)))
- 42664 := ((-((4! + (2^{F(6)}))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 4)
- 42665 := ((F(4!) + 2) + ((6! + F(F(6))) × (-5)))
- 42672 := ((4! × 2) × (6! + (F(7)²)))
- 42674 := (((F(4))!)! - F((-2) + F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(7)) - F(4!)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 42696 &:= (F(4!) - ((2 + F((6 + 9))) \times 6)) \\
 42698 &:= (((F(F((F(4)!))!)^2) \times (F(6) \times 9)) + F(F(8))) \\
 42704 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 270) \times 4) \\
 42714 &:= (F(4!) - ((F((2 + F(7))) - 1) \times F(4)!)) \\
 42720 &:= ((4! \times F((-2) + F(7))) \times 20) \\
 42722 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(2) + (((7^2)^2)))))) \\
 42723 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (2 + ((7^2)^{F(3)}))) \\
 42734 &:= ((4! - F(2)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times F(3!)) - (F(4)!)) \\
 42735 &:= ((F(4!) + 2) - ((7 + (3!)!) \times 5)) \\
 42736 &:= ((4 \times (F((2 + F(7))) - 3!)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 42737 &:= (((((4!)! / (-2)) \times (-7)) / (F(F(3!))!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 42743 &:= ((4! - ((2 - (7^4)))) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 42744 &:= (((F((4!/2)) + 7) \times (-4!)) + F(4!)) \\
 42745 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (((-2) - F(F(7))) + ((F(4)!))!) \times 5)) \\
 42746 &:= (((4! + F(2)) + (7^4)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 42747 &:= ((F(F(4)!))! + ((F((2 + F(7))) \times 4) - F(7))) \\
 42748 &:= (((-F(4)) + F((2 + F(7)))) \times 4) + 8! \\
 42753 &:= ((F(4!) - (2 + F(7))) - (5 \times (3!)!)) \\
 42754 &:= ((F(4!) - (2 \times 7)) - (5 \times ((F(4)!))!)) \\
 42756 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(2) - F(7)) - (5 \times 6!)))) \\
 42759 &:= (F(4!) - (((-((F(2) - (7))))!) \times 5) + 9)) \\
 42760 &:= ((4 \times F((2 + F(7)))) + (F((6 + 0)))!) \\
 \\
 42760 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 0 \\
 42761 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 1 \\
 42762 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 2 \\
 42763 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 3 \\
 42764 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 4 \\
 42765 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 5 \\
 42766 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 6 \\
 42767 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 7 \\
 42768 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 8 \\
 42769 &:= 4 \times F(2 + F(7)) + F(6)! + 9 \\
 \\
 42773 &:= (((4 \times F((2 + F(7)))) + F(7)) + (F(3!)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 42775 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (-((F(2) - 7!) - F((F(7) + (5))))))
42776 := (-((F((4 + (2 × 7))) - 7!)) + (F(6)!))
42777 := ((F(F(4)!))! + ((27 × 7) × F(7)))
42783 := (F(4!) - (F(2) + (7 × (8³))))
42784 := (F(4!) - ((F(2) × 7) × (8^{F(4)})))
42794 := (((4 × F((2 + F(7)))) + F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!))
42795 := (((F(4)!))! + (-2 + F(F(7)))) × (9 × 5))
42796 := ((4 × (F((2 + F(7))) + 9)) + (F(6)!))
42798 := (F(4!) - ((-(2 - 7) × F(9)) × F(8)))
42824 := (-(((F(4) + 2)! + (F(F(8)) / (-2)))) × F((F(4)!))
42827 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((-(F(2) - 8))! / 2) - F(7)))
42828 := (((4! - (-(F(2) - 8))!) / (-2)) + 8!)
42833 := (((F(4!) / 2) - F(F(8))) × F(F(3!))) / 3!
42834 := ((4 + F((2 + 8))) × ((3!)! + (F(4)!))
42835 := (((((F(4) + 2)! × F(8)) + (F(3!))!) - (5))
42838 := (F(4!) - (2 - ((F(8)^{F(3)}) × (-8))))
42840 := (((4 × 2)! + (F(8) × ((4 + 0!)!))
42841 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(2) + (F(8) × ((4 + 1)!))))
42842 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (2 + (8! / (4²))))
42843 := (((((F(4) + 2)! × F(8)) + F(4)) + (F(3!))!)
42845 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(2) + (F(8) × 4!)) × 5))
42846 := (((((F(4) + 2)! × F(8)) + (F(4)!)) + (F(6)!))
42847 := (F(4!) - ((F(2) - (F(8) × 4!)) × (-7)))
42848 := (F(4!) - ((-F(2) + (F(8)^{F(F(4))})) × 8))
42849 := (((4! × 2) + F(8))^{F(F(4))}) × 9)
42853 := ((F(((F(4)! + F(2)))) + ((F(8) × 5!))) + (F(3!))!)
42854 := -((F(F((F(4)!)) - (((F(2) - 8) × (-5))^{F(4)})))
42856 := (((4²) + (F(8) × 5!)) + (F(6)!))
42860 := (4 × ((2 + F(F(8))) - F(F((F(6) - 0!))))
42864 := (((((F(4) + 2)! × F(8)) + (F(6)!)) + (4!))
42865 := (((4! + F(2)) + 8!) + (F(F(6)) × 5!))
42871 := (((4! - F(2)) × 8) × F(F(7))) - 1)
42871 := (-1) + (F(F(7)) × (-8) × (F(2) - 4!))
42872 := (((4! - F(2)) × 8) × F((F(7) × F(2))))

$$\begin{aligned}42873 &:= (((4! - F(2)) \times 8) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(3)) \\42874 &:= (((4! - F(2)) \times 8) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(4)) \\42878 &:= ((F(4))! + (((-2) - F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-8)) \\42883 &:= (((4 \times 2))! - F(8)) + F((F(8) - 3)) \\42884 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(2) - F(8)) + F((F(8) - F(4)))) \\42886 &:= ((F(4!) - F((-2) + F(8))) - ((F(8) - 6!)) \\42892 &:= (((4! / (-2)) + 8!) + F((9 \times 2))) \\42894 &:= -(((F((F(4))!)) + (2 - 8!)) - F((9 \times F(F(4)))) \\42896 &:= ((F(4!) / (F(2) + ((8 + 9)))) + (F(6))! \\42897 &:= (F(4!) - (F(-(F(2) - 8)) \times (F(9) + F(F(7)))) \\42898 &:= -((((F(4))! - F((F(2) + ((8 + 9)))))) - 8!) \\42899 &:= (((-4) - F(2)) + 8!) + F((9 + 9)) \\42902 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (-2) + F((9 \times 02))) \\42903 &:= ((F(((4 - 2) \times 9)) - 0!) + (F(3))!) \\42904 &:= (((4 \times 2))! + F((-9) \times (0! - F(4)))) \\42904 &:= (F(((F(4) - 0!) \times 9)) + ((2 \times 4))! \\42906 &:= ((F(F(4)) + F((2 \times 9))) + (F(06))! \\42907 &:= ((F(4) + F((2 \times 9))) + ((0! + (7)))! \\42908 &:= ((4 + F((2 \times 9))) + (08))! \\42912 &:= ((F((F(4))!)) + F((2 \times 9))) + (F(((1 + 2))!))! \\42913 &:= ((F((F(4))!)) + (F((2 \times 9)) + 1)) + (F(3))! \\42917 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((2 \times 9)) + F((1 \times 7)))) \\42923 &:= ((4! \times 2) + ((F(9) + F(2))^3)) \\42924 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) \times ((2^{9+2} - 4)) \\42925 &:= ((4! + F(2)) \times (F((F(9)/2)) + 5!)) \\42926 &:= (((4! - 2) + F((9 \times 2))) + (F(6))! \\42927 &:= (((F(4!) + 2) + F((F(9)/2))) - (7!)) \\42928 &:= (((4! \times F(2)) + F((9 \times 2))) + 8! \\42930 &:= (((((F(4))!))! \times 2) - 9) \times 30 \\42933 &:= (((F((F(4))!)) + F((2 \times 9))) + F(F(3))) + (F(3))! \\42934 &:= (((F(4))! + F((2 \times 9))) + (F(3))! + (4!)) \\42936 &:= (((4! + F((2 \times 9))) + F(3!)) + (F(6))! \\42938 &:= (((4 \times 2))! + F(9)) + F((-3) + F(8)) \\42946 &:= ((42 + F((9 \times F(F(4)))) + (F(6))! \\42948 &:= (-4) \times (F(F(-(2 - 9))) - (4! + F(F(8))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42952 &:= (((F(4))!) + F((2 \times 9))) \times F((5 + 2)) \\
 42957 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (-2) + (F((9 + 5) \times 7))) \\
 42964 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(2) - (F(9) \times (-6)))) \times 4) \\
 42966 &:= (((F(4)! \times F(-(F(2) - 9))) \times F(F(6))) + (F(6))!) \\
 42967 &:= (((4! + 2) + F(9)) \times 6!) - F(F(7)) \\
 42973 &:= ((F(4!) - 2) - (9 \times F((7 \times F(3))))) \\
 42974 &:= ((F(4!) - F(2)) - (9 \times F((7 \times F(F(4))))) \\
 42976 &:= ((F(4!) + F(2)) - (9 \times F((-7) + F(F(6))))) \\
 42977 &:= (F(4!) - (-2) - (-9) \times F((7 + 7))) \\
 42978 &:= (((F(4))! \times (F(2) + (F(9) \times F(7)))) + 8!) \\
 42984 &:= (((4 \times (2^9)) \times F(8)) - 4!) \\
 42985 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((2^9) + F(8)) \times 5)) \\
 42988 &:= ((4! - 2) \times (F(9) + (8!/F(8)))) \\
 42993 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - (((F(2) - F(9)) \times (9^{F(3)}))) \\
 42996 &:= (((((F(4))!)! \times (F(2) + 9)) - F(9)) \times 6) \\
 43008 &:= (((4^{3!}) / (0! + 0!)) \times F(8)) \\
 43024 &:= (((4 \times F((3! + 0!)))^2) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 43029 &:= -(((F((F(4))!))! - ((F(F(3!))^{0!+2}) \times 9)) \\
 43034 &:= (-(((F(4))!)! + 30)) + (F(F(F(3!))) \times 4) \\
 43034 &:= (-(((F(4))!)! + 30)) + (F(F(F(3!))) \times 4) \\
 43036 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (0! + 3!))) - (6!)) \\
 43043 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (((F(04))!)! + F(F(3!)))) \\
 43044 &:= (((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (0! - ((F(4))!)!)) - F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 43047 &:= (-(((F(4))!)!) + (((F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) \times 4) - F(7))) \\
 43048 &:= (4 \times ((F(3!) \times (0! - 4!)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 43054 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) - 5!) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 43056 &:= (((F(4))!^{3!}) - (05 \times 6!)) \\
 43057 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (((0! + 5))! + 7)) \\
 43058 &:= -(((F(4))! + 3!!) - (-((0! - 5)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 43060 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 0 \\
 43061 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 1 \\
 43062 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 2 \\
 43063 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 3 \\
 43064 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43065 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 5 \\
 43066 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 6 \\
 43067 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 7 \\
 43068 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 8 \\
 43069 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) - 6! + 9 \\
 \\
 43073 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(F((3! + 0!))) + ((7!/F(3)))))) \\
 43074 &:= (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (-((F(3)^{F(07)})) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 43076 &:= ((4 \times (3 + F(F((0! + (7)))))) - (6!)) \\
 43077 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((-((0! - (7))))!) - F(7)) \\
 43084 &:= ((4! - 3!) + ((0! - F(F(8))) \times (-4))) \\
 43086 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (((0! + F(8)) - 6!)) \\
 43092 &:= ((4! + 3) \times (-0! + F((F(9)/2))) \\
 43094 &:= (((4! + 3!) - 0!) \times (F(9) + 4!)) \\
 43096 &:= ((4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(-((0! - 9)))))) - (6!)) \\
 43104 &:= (-(((F(4)!))!) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + 10) \times 4)) \\
 43119 &:= ((-F(4)) \times F((3! + 11))) \times (-9) \\
 43124 &:= (((F(F((F(4)!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(12)) \times (-4)) \\
 43134 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(F(3!)) \times 134)) \\
 43134 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(F(3!)) \times 134)) \\
 43137 &:= (((F(4)!))!) + (F(3!))! + ((1 + F(3!)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 43140 &:= ((F(4) \times (F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times (((F(4)!))! - 0!)) \\
 43144 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(3!) \times (F(14) - 4!))) \\
 43146 &:= ((4! + 3) \times (1 + F((-4) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 43148 &:= (((((F(4)!))! - F((3! + 1))) \times 4) + 8!) \\
 43153 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(15) + F(F(3!)))) \\
 43155 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(F(3!)) \times (15 + 5!))) \\
 43164 &:= (((F(4!) + 3!) \times (1 + F(F(6))))/4!) \\
 43166 &:= (((4 \times (3!))! - F((1 + F(6)))) + (F(6)!)) \\
 43167 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) - ((F(F(F(6))) + 7))) \\
 43168 &:= ((4 \times ((3!)! - F((1 \times 6)))) + 8!) \\
 43172 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(3) \times F(17)) + 2)) \\
 43173 &:= ((4! + 3) \times (F(17) + F(3))) \\
 43174 &:= (F(4!) - ((3! \times F(17))/F(4))) \\
 43176 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(3!) + F((-1 + F(7)))) \times F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43178 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 1)) - F((7 + 8))) \\
 43180 &:= (((F(4) \times (3!)!) - 1) \times (F(8) - 0!)) \\
 43182 &:= -((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (F(3!) \times (-1 - F((F(8) - F(2))))))) \\
 43183 &:= (((4 \times ((3!)! + 1)) - (F(8))) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 43184 &:= (F(4!) - 3184) \\
 43185 &:= (F(4) \times (((3!)! \times (-1 + F(8))) - (5))) \\
 43187 &:= ((4 \times (3!)!) - ((-1) \times 8!) + F(7)) \\
 43190 &:= (((F(4))! \times (3!)! - 1) \times (9 + 0!)) \\
 43194 &:= (((F(4))! \times (3!)! \times (1 + 9)) - (F(4))!) \\
 43195 &:= (((F(4))! \times (3!)! \times (1 + 9)) - (5)) \\
 43197 &:= ((-F(4)) \times ((3!)! + 1)) - (-9) \times 7!)) \\
 43198 &:= (((4!^3) + (-((1 - 9)))!) - F(F(8))) \\
 \\
 43200 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 0 \\
 43201 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 1 \\
 43202 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 2 \\
 43203 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 3 \\
 43204 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 4 \\
 43205 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 5 \\
 43206 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 6 \\
 43207 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 7 \\
 43208 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 8 \\
 43209 &:= 4 \times 3!! + F((2 + 0!)!)! + 9 \\
 \\
 43210 &:= (((F(4))! \times (3!)! + F(2)) \times 10) \\
 43212 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(2) - F(12)))))) \\
 43215 &:= (((4 \times (3!)!) + F(2)) \times 15) \\
 43218 &:= (((F(4!)/F(3!))/2) + ((1 \times 8)!)) \\
 43220 &:= (((F(4) \times (3!)!) + F(2)) \times 20) \\
 43224 &:= (4! + (((3 + 2)!^2) \times F(4))) \\
 43225 &:= (((F(4!)) + (F(3!)!)/2) + (F(2) - 5!)) \\
 43227 &:= (((F(4))!)! + (F(3!)!) + (F((2 + 2)^7))) \\
 43230 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times (3!)!) + F(2)) \times 30) \\
 43232 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(3!) \times (F(2) + 3!))^2)) \\
 43234 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((3^2)) - ((3!)! \times (-4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 43234 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((3²)) - ((3!)! × (-4))))
- 43235 := ((F(4!) - F(3!)) - ((2 + 3)⁵))
- 43236 := ((4 × ((3²)³) + (F(6))!)
- 43238 := (((-F((F(4)!)) - F((F(F(3!)) - F(2)))) × (-F(3!))) - F(F(8)))
- 43240 := (((F(4) × (3!)! + 2) × (F(F((F(4)!)) - 0!))
- 43242 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F(3!)) - (-2) × ((F(4)!))!) × 2))
- 43243 := (F(4!) - ((3 + 2)^{F(4)+F(3)}))
- 43244 := (((F(4)^{3!}) + 2) × 4) + (F((F(4)!))!)
- 43245 := (F(4!) - (3 + ((2 + 4!) × 5!)))
- 43246 := (((F(4)!))! + (F(3!))! + (-2) + (F(4!)/F(F(6))))
- 43247 := (F(4!) - (((3!)! + 2) × 4) + F(F(7)))
- 43252 := -(F((F(4)!)) - (((3!)! + F(2)) × (5!/2)))
- 43254 := -(((F(4)! - (((3!)! + F(2)) × 5!)/F(F(4))))
- 43255 := (F(4!) - ((3! × (-2)) + (5⁵)))
- 43256 := (4 × (((3! × (-2)) - 5!) + F(F(F(6))))
- 43259 := (((F(4)!))! + (((3!)! + F(2)) × 59))
- 43261 := -(((F(4)!))! - (((3!)! + F(2)) × 61))
- 43262 := -(F(F(4)) - ((F(3!) × 26)²))
- 43263 := (((((F(4) + F(3)))!)² + F(F(6))) × 3)
- 43264 := (((4! + F(3))²) × 64)
- 43267 := (F(4!) - (((3! + F(2)) - (F(6)!)) / (-F(7))))
- 43271 := ((4 × (F(F(F(3!))) - (2⁷))) - 1)
- 43272 := (F((F(4)!)) + (((F(3!) × (2 × F(7)))²)))
- 43273 := (F(4!) - (((F(F(3!)))²) × 7) + F(3!))
- 43274 := ((((((F(4)!))! / 3) - 2) × (-F(7))) + F(4!))
- 43275 := (((4!^{F(3)}) + F(2)) × 75)
- 43276 := (4 × (-(((3 + 2)! + 7)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 43278 := ((F((F(4)!)) × (F((F(F(3!)) - F(2))) + F(7))) - F(F(8)))
- 43280 := ((F(4) × F((F(3!) × 2))) + ((8! - 0!)))
- 43281 := ((F(4) × F((F(3!) × 2))) + ((8 × 1)!))
- 43282 := ((F(4) × F((F(3!) × 2))) + ((8! + F(2))))
- 43283 := ((F(F(4)) + (F(3!))!) + (F((2 × 8)) × 3))
- 43284 := (F(4!) - (3! × (2 + (8^{F(4)}))))
- 43288 := ((4 × ((3!)! + (F(2) + F(8)))) + 8!)

$$\begin{aligned}
 43289 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/2) - (F(8) + F(9))) \\
 43290 &:= (F(4!) - (3! \times ((2^9) + 0!))) \\
 43293 &:= (F(4!) - ((3! \times (2^9)) + 3)) \\
 43294 &:= ((F(4!) - (3! \times (2^9))) - F(F(4))) \\
 43296 &:= (F(4!) - (32 \times 96)) \\
 43297 &:= (((F(4!) - 3!) - F((2 \times 9))) + F(F(7))) \\
 43300 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (((3! - 0!)! + 0!))) \\
 43302 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (((3! - 0!)!))) - 2) \\
 43303 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (((3! - 0!)!))) - F(F(3))) \\
 43304 &:= ((F((4! - 3)) - ((3! - 0!)!) \times 4) \\
 43308 &:= (F(4!) - (((3!)! / F(3!)) \times F((0! + 8)))) \\
 43309 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - (0! + F(9))) \\
 43312 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (((3! - 1)! - 2))) \\
 43316 &:= (4 \times ((3 - ((3! - 1)!) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 43317 &:= -((((F(4)!)! - (F(F(3!)) \times ((F(3!) + 1) \times F(F(7)))))) \\
 43318 &:= ((F((4! - 3!)) \times F(F(3!))) + (-1 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 43320 &:= ((F(F(4)) + 3!) \times (3 \times 20)) \\
 43322 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - 22) \\
 43323 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - F(2^3)) \\
 43324 &:= (((-((F(4!) + F(3!))) - (F(3!)!)/(-2)) - (4!)) \\
 43326 &:= ((F(4)!) \times (((3!)! \times (F(3!) + 2)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 43327 &:= (((-((F(4!) - F(3!))) - (F(3!)!)/(-2)) - F(7)) \\
 43328 &:= (4 \times ((3! - ((3 + 2)!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 43331 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - F((3! + 1))) \\
 43332 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - (3! \times 2)) \\
 43333 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - (3 + F(3!))) \\
 43334 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - (3! + (4))) \\
 43334 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) - (3! + (4))) \\
 43335 &:= ((4! + F(F(3!))) \times ((3!)! + ((3^5)))) \\
 43336 &:= ((F(((4 + 3) \times F(3))) \times F(3!)) + (F(6)!) \\
 43337 &:= (((F(4!) + (F((3 + 3)))!)/F(3)) - 7) \\
 43338 &:= ((F(4!) - 3!) - (F((F(3) \times 3!)) \times F(8))) \\
 43339 &:= (((-((F(4!) + F(3!))) - (F(3!)!)/(-F(3))) - 9) \\
 43340 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43341 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 1 \\
 43342 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 2 \\
 43343 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 3 \\
 43344 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 4 \\
 43345 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 5 \\
 43346 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 6 \\
 43347 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 7 \\
 43348 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 8 \\
 43349 &:= (F(4!) + F(3!)!)/F(3) - 4 + 9 \\
 \\
 43350 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) + (5 + 0!)) \\
 43352 &:= (F(4!) - (F(3!) \times F((F(3) \times (5 + 2)))))) \\
 43353 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) + (F(3!)!)) + (F((F(3) \times 5))^{F(3)})) \\
 43354 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) + (5 \times F(F(4)))) \\
 43355 &:= (F(((4 + 3) \times F(3))) \times (5! - (5))) \\
 43356 &:= (((4 \times (3^{3!})) + 5!) + (F(6)!)) \\
 43357 &:= (F(4!) - (((3 \times 3)!/5!) - F(7))) \\
 43360 &:= (((F(4) \times (3!)!) + F(3!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)) \\
 43362 &:= (((F(4!) + (3!^{F(3)})) + (F(6)!)/2) \\
 43363 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) + (F(F(6)) - F(3))) \\
 43364 &:= -((((F((4 + 3!)^{F(3)} - F(F(6))) - F(4!))) \\
 43365 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(3!))) - (((3 + 6)!/5!)) \\
 43366 &:= (((F((4 + 3!)^{F(3)} + F(F(6))) + (F(6)!)) \\
 43367 &:= (4! - (F((3 + F(3!))) \times (-6! + F(F(7)))))) \\
 43368 &:= (F(4!) - (F(3!) \times (-F(3) - F((6 + 8)))))) \\
 43372 &:= (((-F(4!)) - (F(3!)!)) - (F(3!) \times 7))/(-2) \\
 43373 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(3!))) - (F(3!) \times F((7 \times F(3)))))) \\
 43374 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(3!)^3) - F(7)) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 43375 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F(3)) + F((F(3) + F(7)))) \times 5)) \\
 43376 &:= (F(4!) - ((-3) + F((F(3) \times 7))) \times F(6)) \\
 43377 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(3))) - ((-3) + F(F(7))) \times F(7)) \\
 43378 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(3!)!)/F(3)) + (F(7) + F(8))) \\
 43380 &:= ((F(4) + 3!!) \times (3 \times (F(8) - 0!))) \\
 43383 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(3!) + F((F(3) \times 8))) \times 3)) \\
 43384 &:= ((-(((4 + 3!)^{F(3)} + F(F(8))) \times 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 43385 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((-3) - F(-(3! - F(8)))) × (-5))
- 43386 := ((F(4!) - 3!) - (3! × F((8 + 6))))
- 43388 := (4 × (((3!)/(-3!)) + F(F(8))) + (F(8)))
- 43389 := (((4 × (3!))! + (F(3!))!) + (F(8) × 9))
- 43391 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((3! × (F(3)⁹)) - 1))
- 43392 := (((F(4)! × (F(3!)³)) + ((9 - F(2)))!)
- 43393 := ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(3!))!) + ((F(3)⁹) × 3!))
- 43394 := (((4^{3!}) - 3!) + (F(9)^{F(4)}))
- 43395 := ((4 × (F(F(F(3!))) - 3)) - (F((9 + 5))))
- 43396 := ((4 + (3! × (F(3)⁹))) + (F(6))!)
- 43398 := ((F(4)! + (((3! × (F(3)⁹)) + 8!)))
- 43399 := (((F(4) + F(3))^{F(3!)}) - F(9))/9
- 43403 := (-F(((F(4)! + F(3!)))) + (4 × (-0! + F(F(F(3!))))))
- 43404 := (F(4!) + ((F((F(3)⁴)) + 0!) × (-F(4)))
- 43406 := (((F(F((F(4)!))³)/F(4)) - (0! - (F(6))!))
- 43407 := ((F(4!) - F((3! × F(4)))) - F((0! + F(7))))
- 43408 := (((F(F((F(4)!))³)/F(4)) + (0! + 8!))
- 43410 := ((F(F((F(4)!))!) + ((3!)! × (F(4)!)) × 10)
- 43416 := (F(4!) - (-3) × (F(4) - F(16)))
- 43417 := (F(4!) - ((-3!) + F(F(((F(4)! + 1)))) × F(7)))
- 43422 := ((4 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (((F(4)!)/2) + 2))
- 43423 := ((4 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (((F(4)!)/2) + 2)/F(3))
- 43424 := (F(4!) - (((3!)! + 4²) × 4)
- 43425 := (((F(F((F(4)!))³) - 4²) × 5)
- 43427 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((3!)/F(4)) - F(2)) × F(7))
- 43428 := (((4! × F(3)) - 4) × F((2 × 8)))
- 43432 := (((F(4)! - F(3!)) × (-F(4) + (F(3!)²)))
- 43433 := (((F(4!) + (F(3!))!)/F(F(4))) + F((3 + F(3))))
- 43434 := ((-F(4!))/F(F(3!))) - (((F(4)! + 3!) - F(4!)))
- 43434 := ((-F(4!))/F(F(3!))) - (((F(4)! + 3!) - F(4!)))
- 43435 := ((-F(4!))/F(F(3!))) + (((F(4!) - 3!) - (5)))
- 43436 := (((4! + F(F(3!))) × (F(F(4)) + 3!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 43437 := ((F(4!) - 3!) - (4! + 3⁷))
- 43438 := ((F(4!)/3!) + (((F(4)!^{3!}) - F(F(8))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 43439 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (4 \times F(F(3!)))))) - 9) \\
 43440 &:= (((4 + 3!)/F(F(4))) \times ((4 + 0!)!)) \\
 43441 &:= (((-(F(4!))/F(F(3!))) - ((F(4)!)!) + (F(4!) + 1)) \\
 43442 &:= (((-(F(4!))/F(F(3!))) - ((F(4)!)!) + ((F(4!) + 2))) \\
 43443 &:= (F(4!) - (((3 + 4!)!/(4!)!)/3!)) \\
 43444 &:= (((-(4) \times (3!)!) + F(4!)) - 44) \\
 43445 &:= ((-(43) + F(4!)) - ((4! \times 5!))) \\
 43446 &:= (F(4!) - (3! + (4 \times (F(4)^6)))) \\
 43447 &:= (((4^{F(3)})!)/((F(4) \times 4)!) - F(F(7))) \\
 43448 &:= (4 \times (F((-3) + 4!)) + (-4) \times F(8))) \\
 43449 &:= (((-(F(4!))/F(F(3!))) - ((F(4)!)!) + ((F(4!) + 9))) \\
 43452 &:= (F(4!) - ((3! \times (4 + 5))^2)) \\
 43453 &:= (F(4!) - (F((3! + (4))) \times 53)) \\
 43454 &:= (F(4!) - (34 + (5! \times 4!))) \\
 43455 &:= (((F(4!)/3) - (F((4 \times 5)))) \times 5) \\
 43456 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(3) + 4!) \times (5! - F(6)))) \\
 43457 &:= (4! + (((3!)! / F(F(4))) \times 5!) + F(F(7))) \\
 43458 &:= (-((F(F(4))^{F(3!)})) + ((F((F(4)!)^5) + F(F(8)))) \\
 43459 &:= (((-(4) \times (3!)!) + F(4!)) + (5 - F(9))) \\
 43461 &:= ((F(4!) - 3!) - (F(4)^{6+1})) \\
 43462 &:= ((F(4!) - F(3!)) - (F(4!)/(F(6) \times 2))) \\
 43463 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(3))) - (4 \times (6! + 3!))) \\
 43464 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(3) + (4)) + 6!) \times 4)) \\
 43465 &:= (F(4!) - (3 + (4 \times (6! + (5)))))) \\
 43466 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(3) - (-4) \times (-6 - 6!)))) \\
 43467 &:= ((F(4!) - F(3!)) - ((4 \times 6!) + F(7))) \\
 43468 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(3))) - ((4 \times 6!) + F(8))) \\
 43470 &:= (F(4!) - (F(F(3!)) \times (-((F(4)!) - F((F(7) - 0!)))))) \\
 43471 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((4! \times F(7)) + 1)) \\
 43472 &:= ((F((F(4)!) + ((F(3!)!)/(-4!))) \times (F(7) \times (-2))) \\
 43473 &:= (((-(4) \times (3!)!) + F(4!)) - (F(7) + F(3))) \\
 43474 &:= (F(4!) - (((3!)! \times F(F(4))) + 7) \times F(F(4))) \\
 43475 &:= (((F(4)!)! + (F(3!)!) - (((F(4)!)! - F(F(7))) \times (-5))) \\
 43476 &:= (F(4!) - ((3 \times 4) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$43477 := (F(4!) - (((3!)! / 4) + F(F(7))) \times 7)$$

$$43479 := (F(4!) - (-3) \times (4! - F((7 + 9))))$$

$$43480 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 0$$

$$43481 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 1$$

$$43482 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 2$$

$$43483 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 3$$

$$43484 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 4$$

$$43485 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 5$$

$$43486 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 6$$

$$43487 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 7$$

$$43488 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 8$$

$$43489 := F(4!) - 3!! \times 4 - 8 + 9$$

$$43490 := ((-(4!^3)) + F(4!)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))$$

$$43491 := (F(4!) - (F(F(3!)) \times ((4 \times F(9)) + 1)))$$

$$43492 := (4 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F((F(4)!)) \times 9) + F(2)))$$

$$43493 := ((F((F(4)!))! - ((F(F(3!)) - ((F(F(4)) \times F((F(9)/F(3))))))))$$

$$43494 := (F(4!) + ((3! - (4! \times ((9 - 4)!))))$$

$$43496 := (((-4) \times (3!)! + F(4!)) + F(((9 - 6)!))$$

$$43497 := (((F(4) \times (3!)! + F(4!)) - (-9) + 7!))$$

$$43498 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (F(3) \times (F((F(4)! - F((9 + 8)))))))$$

$$43499 := (((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + F(F((F(4)!))) - (9 \times F(9)))$$

$$43504 := ((F(4!) - F(3!)) - ((5! - 0!) \times 4!))$$

$$43509 := ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (5 \times F((0! + 9))))$$

$$43514 := (F(4!) + ((F(3) - ((5! - 1) \times 4!)))$$

$$43523 := ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (5 + (2^{F(3!)})))$$

$$43524 := (((F((-4) + F(F(3!)))) + (5)) \times 2) + (F((F(4)!))!)$$

$$43527 := ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((5! - F((2 \times 7))))$$

$$43531 := (((F(4))!^{3!}) - (5^{3!-1}))$$

$$43532 := ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! + 3!) \times 2))$$

$$43533 := ((((-4!) + 3!!) - (5)) \times 3) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$43534 := (F(4!) - (F(3) + ((5! - F(3)) \times 4!))$$

$$43534 := (F(4!) - (F(3) + ((5! - F(3)) \times 4!))$$

$$43536 := -(((4! + F(3)) \times 5!) - (3!^6))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43537 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! \times F(3)) + (7))) \\
 43538 &:= (((F(4!)/(-3!)) + F(F((5 + 3)))) + 8!) \\
 43539 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - ((F(F(3!)) - (5! \times (3 \times 9)))))) \\
 43540 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - ((5!/F(F(4))) + 0!))) \\
 43542 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! \times F(F(4))) + 2)) \\
 43543 &:= ((F(4!) + F((F(3) \times 5))) + (-4) \times (3!)!) \\
 43544 &:= ((F(4!) + F(3!)) - ((5! - F(F(4))) \times 4!)) \\
 43545 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! - F(F(F(4)))) + 5!)) \\
 43546 &:= ((F(F(4)) - ((F(3) \times 5!))) + (4 \times F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 43547 &:= (F(4!) - (((-3) + 5!) \times 4!) + F(7)) \\
 43548 &:= (((F(4) + 3!) \times (5! - 4)) - 8!) \\
 43551 &:= (F(4) \times (-3) + (5! \times (5! + 1))) \\
 43552 &:= -((F((F(4)!)) - ((3 \times 5!) \times (5! + F(2)))))) \\
 43554 &:= (((F(4) - (-3) \times 5!) \times 5!) - (F(4)!)) \\
 43555 &:= (((F(4) - (-3) \times 5!) \times 5!) - (5)) \\
 43557 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! + 5!) - F(7))) \\
 43559 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5 \times 5) \times 9)) \\
 \\
 43560 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 0 \\
 43561 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 1 \\
 43562 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 2 \\
 43563 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 3 \\
 43564 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 4 \\
 43565 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 5 \\
 43566 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 6 \\
 43567 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 7 \\
 43568 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 8 \\
 43569 &:= (4! + 3) \times 5! + F(6)! + 9 \\
 \\
 43570 &:= (((4! \times F(3!)) - (5)) \times F(F(7))) - 0! \\
 43571 &:= (((4! \times F(3!)) - (5)) \times F(F((7 \times 1)))) \\
 43572 &:= (((4! \times F(3!)) - (5)) \times F(F(7))) + F(2) \\
 43573 &:= (((4! \times F(3!)) - (5)) \times F(F(7))) + F(3) \\
 43574 &:= ((4 \times F(F((3 + 5)))) - (7!/4!)) \\
 43575 &:= (((4!^{F(3)}) + (5)) \times 75)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 43576 := (((4^{3!}) - (5! × 7)) + (F(6))!)
- 43577 := (((((F(4))!)! / F(3)) × 5!) + (F((7 + 7))))
- 43578 := (F(4!) - (-3) + ((5! + F(7)) × F(8)))
- 43579 := ((4 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (-5) × (-7 - F(9)))
- 43582 := ((4 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (5! + (82)))
- 43586 := (((-(4³) × 5!) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!)
- 43589 := ((F(4) + F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! × (-8)) × F(9)))
- 43592 := (4 × (F(F(F(3!))) - ((-(5 - 9))! × 2)))
- 43593 := ((4 × F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5 × F(9)) + F(F(3!))))
- 43594 := (((4! × (3 - 5!)) + F(9)) + F(4!))
- 43595 := (((F(4))!)! + (35^{F(9-5)}))
- 43596 := (F(4!) - (3 × ((5! + F(9)) × 6)))
- 43597 := ((4 × (F(F(F(3!))) - (5 × 9))) - 7)
- 43604 := (((-(4!) - F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 04)
- 43608 := (4 × ((-(F(3)) × (F(F(6)) + 0!)) + F(F(8))))
- 43611 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F(11)))
- 43614 := (((4! × F(F(3!))) + F((F(F(6)) - 1))) × (F(4))!)
- 43615 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((3!)! - 61) × 5)
- 43616 := (4 × ((-(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((1 + F(6)))))
- 43618 := ((F((4! + 3!)) + (F(6))!) / (-1 + F(8)))
- 43619 := (F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (3 × (F(F(F(6))) - F((1 + 9)))))
- 43620 := (((F(4) × (3!)!) + F(F(6))) × 20)
- 43623 := (((F((4! - 3!)) + (F(6))!) - F(2)) + 3!!)
- 43624 := (F(4!) - ((F(3) + (6 × 2))^{F(4)}))
- 43626 := ((F((4! - 3!)) + (F(6))!) - (-2 - 6!))
- 43627 := (((F(4))!^{3!}) - (F((F(6) - F(2))) × F(F(7))))
- 43630 := (F(4!) - ((-3!) - F(F(F(6)))) / (-3 - 0!))
- 43632 := (((4!³) + 6!) × 3) × F(2)
- 43633 := (((F(4)^{3!}) + (F(6))!) + F((3 × 3!)))
- 43634 := (((4!³) + 6!) × 3) + F(F(4))
- 43634 := (((4!³) + 6!) × 3) + F(F(4))
- 43635 := (F(4) × ((-F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((3!)! × 5))
- 43636 := (((4^{F(3!)}) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(3!) - F(F(F(6))))
- 43637 := (F(4!) - (((3! + F(6))³) - F(7)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 43638 &:= ((F(4!)/(3! + F(6))) + (3! + 8!)) \\
 43639 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F((6 + 3)))) - 9) \\
 43640 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 0 \\
 43641 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 1 \\
 43642 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 2 \\
 43643 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 3 \\
 43644 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 4 \\
 43645 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 5 \\
 43646 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 6 \\
 43647 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 7 \\
 43648 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 8 \\
 43649 &:= (-F(4)! \times 3! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4 + 9 \\
 43650 &:= (((-4) \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))))) - 50) \\
 43651 &:= ((4 \times (-3) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((5! + 1))) \\
 43652 &:= (4 \times ((-F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (5^2)) \\
 43653 &:= (((-F(4!)) + F(F(3!))) - (6! \times (-5^3))) \\
 43654 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(3) + F(F(6))) \times (5! - F(F(4))))) \\
 43655 &:= ((4 \times (-F(F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (-5 - 5!)) \\
 43656 &:= (F(4!) - ((F((3 \times 6)) + 5!) + F(6))) \\
 43657 &:= (F(4!) - ((F((3 \times 6)) + 5!) + (7))) \\
 43658 &:= (((F(4!)/(-3!)) + (F(6)! + 5!) + F(F(8))) \\
 43659 &:= (F(4!) - (F((F(3) + (6))) \times (5! + 9))) \\
 43660 &:= (4 \times ((3 + F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(6) + 0!)))) \\
 43662 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((6!/6) + 2)) \\
 43663 &:= ((4 \times (-F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(6) + 3))) \\
 43664 &:= ((F(4!) - F((3 \times 6))) - ((F(6) - F(4))!)) \\
 43665 &:= (((F(4)! + (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) - 5!)))) \\
 43666 &:= (((4^3) - (6)) \times F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 43667 &:= (((4^{F(3)})!)/((6 + 6)! - F(7)) \\
 43669 &:= (F(F((F(4)!)) + (-((F(3) - (6))) \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(9)))) \\
 43671 &:= (((-4) \times ((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) + 7)) - 1) \\
 43672 &:= ((F(4!) - F(3!)) + ((F(6)!)/(-F(7) + 2))) \\
 43673 &:= (F(4!) - (F((F(3) + F(6))) \times (7^{F(3)})))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 43674 := (((F(4!)/(-3!)) - (6 - 7!)) + F(4!))
 43675 := (F(4!) - (((F(3!))!/(F(6) + (7))) + (5)))
 43677 := (-F(4) + (((F(3) × F(6))!/(F(7))!) × F(7)))
 43678 := ((F(4!) - F(3)) + ((F(6))!/(-(7 + 8))))
 43679 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(7) - F(9))))
 43680 := ((4! - (-3) × 6!) × (F(8) - 0!))
 43681 := (F(4!) - (((F(3!))!/(-(6) + F(8))) - 1))
 43682 := (F(4!) - (((F(3!))!/(-(6) + F(8))) - 2))
 43683 := ((F(4!) + 3) - ((F(6))!/(F(8) - 3!)))
 43684 := ((-((4! + (3!/6))) + F(F(8))) × 4)
 43685 := (F(4!) - ((F((3 × 6)) - F(8)) + 5!))
 43686 := F(4)! × ((3 - 6)⁸ + 6!)
 43687 := (F(4!) - ((3! + F((6 + 8))) × 7))
 43689 := ((-4!) + (F(3!))!) + (F((6 + 8)) × 9))
 43690 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (9 + 0!))
 43691 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (9 × 1))
 43692 := (F(4!) - (F((3 × 6)) + (92)))
 43693 := (F((F(4))!) + (((F(3!)⁶) - F(9))/3!))
 43694 := (F((F(4))!) + (3! × (6! + (9⁴))))
 43695 := ((F(4!) + (F((-F(3) + F(F(6)))) × (-9))) × 5)
 43696 := (((4^{3!}) + (F(6))!) - (((9 - 6))!))
 43697 := (-F(4) + ((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) × (9 - F(7))))
 43698 := (F(4!) - (F((3 + F(6))) × (9 + F(8))))
 43699 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (9/9))
- 43700 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 0
 43701 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 1
 43702 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 2
 43703 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 3
 43704 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 4
 43705 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 5
 43706 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 6
 43707 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 7
 43708 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 8
 43709 := 4 × (-F(F(3!)) + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 9

- 43712** := $((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (71 + F(2)))$
43713 := $((F(4)^{F(3)}) \times F((F(7) + 1))) + (F(3!))!$
43714 := $((-F(4)) \times (F(F(3!)) - (7!))) + (F((-1 + 4!)))$
43715 := $((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((7 + 1)^5))$
43716 := $(F(4!) - ((3! \times F(7)) \times F((1 + F(6))))$
43719 := $((F(4)!) + (F(3!)!) - (F((F(7) + 1)) \times (-9)))$
43722 := $(F(4!) - (3! \times (F((7 + F(2)))^2)))$
43723 := $((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(7))) - (F(2) + F(3!)))$
43724 := $((F((4! - 3)) - (F(7) + 2)) \times 4)$
43725 := $(F(4!) - (((3! + 7!)/2) + 5!))$
43726 := $(-((F(4)!) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - F(7)) \times (-2 - 6))))$
43727 := $(F(4!) - (F(3) + (7 \times F((2 \times 7))))$
43729 := $(F(4!) - (F((3 + 7)) + F((2 \times 9))))$
43730 := $((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F((7 + 3)) - 0!))$
43731 := $(-F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - F(7)) \times (3 + 1))$
43732 := $((4! + F(3)) \times ((7!/3) + 2))$
43733 := $((((F((F(4)!)^{3!}) + F(F(7))) + F(F(3!)))/3!))$
43734 := $((F(4)!)^{3!} + ((F(F(7)) - 3!) \times (F(4)!))$
43734 := $((F(4)!)^{3!} + ((F(F(7)) - 3!) \times (F(4)!))$
43736 := $(-4) \times ((3! - F((7 \times 3))) + (6))$
43737 := $((F(4!) + F(3!)) - (7 \times F((F(3) \times 7))))$
43738 := $((4 \times ((F(3)^{F(7)} + 3!)) + F(F(8)))$
43739 := $(F(4!) - ((3! + F(F(7))) \times (F(3) + 9)))$
43741 := $((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((7 \times (F(4)!) + 1))$
43743 := $(F(4!) - (F(F(3!)) \times ((7 - F(F(4)))^3)))$
43744 := $(((-4) + F((3 \times 7))) \times 4) - 4!$
43745 := $((F((4! - 3)) - (F(7)^{F(4)})) \times 5)$
43746 := $((F(F(4)) - 3!) - F(F(7))) \times (-46)$
43747 := $((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) - 4!) - F(7)$
43748 := $((F((4! - 3)) - 7) \times 4) - 8$
43750 := $((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((7 \times 5) - 0!))$
43751 := $((4 \times (-F(3!)) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) - 1$
43752 := $(4 \times (F((3 \times 7)) - F(((5 - 2)!)))$
43753 := $((4 \times (-F(3!)) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) + F(F(3))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43754 &:= ((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) - (5!/4)) \\
 43755 &:= ((4 \times (-3!) + F(F((F(7) - (5)))))) - (5)) \\
 43759 &:= (F(4) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - 7) \times (-(5 - 9)))) \\
 43768 &:= (((4!^{F(3)}) \times 76) - 8) \\
 43770 &:= (((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) - F(7)) - 0!) \\
 43776 &:= ((-4) \times (3!)!) + (((-7) + F(7))^6)) \\
 43777 &:= ((F(4!) - F((3 \times (-7) + F(7)))) - 7) \\
 43778 &:= ((F(4!) - 3!) - F(((F(7) + F(7)) - 8))) \\
 43779 &:= ((F(4!) - F(3)) - (F(7) \times (F(F(7)) - F(9)))) \\
 43780 &:= (4 \times (F((3 \times 7)) - ((8 \times 0)!)) \\
 43783 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(3))) - F(((7 + 8) + 3))) \\
 43790 &:= ((F(4)!) + (-((3 - 7) \times F(F((9 - 0!)))))) \\
 43793 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(3) + (7))) - F((9 \times F(3)))) \\
 43794 &:= (((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) + F(9)) - 4!) \\
 43795 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((7 + 9) - 5)) \\
 43797 &:= (((((4^{F(3)})!) / (F(7)!) + 9) \times F(7)) \\
 43798 &:= (((F(4)!) + F(3!)) + ((F(7) - 9) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 43799 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(3) + F(7)) - F((9 + 9)))))) \\
 \\
 43800 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 0 \\
 43801 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 1 \\
 43802 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 2 \\
 43803 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 3 \\
 43804 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 4 \\
 43805 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 5 \\
 43806 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 6 \\
 43807 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 7 \\
 43808 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 8 \\
 43809 &:= 4 \times (3 + F(F(8)) + 0!) + 9 \\
 \\
 43810 &:= ((4 \times (3! + F(F(8)))) + (1 + 0!)) \\
 43811 &:= ((4 \times ((3! + F(F(8))) + 1)) - 1) \\
 43812 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (((3! + F(F(8))) + 1) \times 2)) \\
 43813 &:= (-(F(4)) + ((F(3!) + F(F(8))) \times (1 + 3))) \\
 43814 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((3! + F(F(8))) + 1) \times 4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$43815 := ((4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)))) - (1^5))$$

$$43817 := ((4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)))) + (1^7))$$

$$43818 := ((F(4!) - F((-3) + F(8))) + F((1 + 8)))$$

$$43819 := ((F(4!) - F((-3) + F(8))) + (1 + F(9)))$$

$$43820 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 0$$

$$43821 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 1$$

$$43822 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 2$$

$$43823 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 3$$

$$43824 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 4$$

$$43825 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 5$$

$$43826 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 6$$

$$43827 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 7$$

$$43828 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 8$$

$$43829 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(2)) + 9$$

$$43830 := (((F(F(4)) \times (3!)!) + (F(8))) \times 30)$$

$$43831 := ((4 \times ((3! + F(F(8))) + 3!)) - 1)$$

$$43833 := ((4 \times ((3! + F(F(8))) + 3!)) + F(F(3)))$$

$$43834 := (((4 + 3!) \times (-F(8)))/3!) + F(4!)$$

$$43834 := (((4 + 3!) \times (-F(8)))/3!) + F(4!)$$

$$43837 := ((4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)))) + (3 \times 7))$$

$$43838 := (((4! - 3!) + F(F(8))) \times 3) + F(F(8))$$

$$43839 := ((F(4!) + F((F(3) + 8))) - F((F(3) \times 9)))$$

$$43840 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 0$$

$$43841 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 1$$

$$43842 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 2$$

$$43843 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 3$$

$$43844 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 4$$

$$43845 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 5$$

$$43846 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 6$$

$$43847 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 7$$

$$43848 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 8$$

$$43849 := 4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)) + F(4!)) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43850 &:= (F(4!) - (-3) + ((F(8) \times 5!) + 0!)) \\
 43851 &:= (F(4!) - (-3) - ((F(8) \times 5!) \times (-1))) \\
 43852 &:= (F(4!) - (-3) + ((F(8) \times 5!) - F(2))) \\
 43853 &:= (F(4!) - (-3) + ((F(8) \times 5!) - F(3))) \\
 43854 &:= (F(4!) - (-3) + ((F(8) \times 5!) - F(4))) \\
 43855 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(3) - ((F(8) \times 5!) - (5)))) \\
 43857 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(3) - ((F(8) \times 5!) - (7)))) \\
 43858 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(3) - ((F(8) \times 5!) - 8))) \\
 43859 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(3) - ((F(8) \times 5!) - 9))) \\
 43860 &:= (((F(4) + 3!) + 8) \times 60) \\
 43863 &:= ((4 \times (3! + F(F(8)))) + F((F(6) + F(3)))) \\
 43864 &:= (((4! + F(3)) + F(F(8))) - 6) \times 4 \\
 43866 &:= ((4 \times (-F(3)) + F(F(8))) + (6!/F(6))) \\
 43867 &:= (((F(4!)/3!) + 8!) - F((6 + F(7)))) \\
 43870 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (87 - 0!)) \\
 43871 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (87 \times 1)) \\
 43872 &:= (4! \times ((3 \times F((8 + 7))) - 2)) \\
 43873 &:= ((F(4!) - F((-3) + F(8))) + F((F(7) - F(3)))) \\
 43874 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(3) - ((8 \times F(7)) \times 4!))) \\
 43875 &:= (((-4!) + 3!) - F(8)) \times (F(7) \times 5) \\
 43877 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) + (F(3)!)) + ((F(8) \times F(7)) \times F(7))) \\
 43879 &:= ((4 \times (F(3!) + F(F(8)))) + (7 \times 9)) \\
 43884 &:= ((F(4!) - 3!) + (F(8) \times (-84))) \\
 43886 &:= ((4 \times (-3!) + F(F(8))) + (F(8) \times 6)) \\
 43887 &:= ((4 \times ((F(3!) + F(8)) + F(F(8)))) - F(7)) \\
 43890 &:= (((F(4)!))! + F(-(3! - F(8)))) \times (F(9) - 0!) \\
 43892 &:= (4 \times ((3! + F(F(8))) + F((9 - F(2)))) \\
 43893 &:= ((4 \times ((-3!) + F(F(8))) + F(9)) - 3) \\
 43895 &:= ((F(4!) - F((-3) + F(8))) - (9 - 5!)) \\
 43896 &:= -((4! - ((3! + F(8)) + F(9)) \times 6!)) \\
 43898 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(8)))) + (9 + F(8))) \\
 43903 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(9) + 0!))) - (F(F(3!)))) \\
 43904 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (((3 \times 9) + 0!)^{F(4)}) \\
 43905 &:= ((F(4!) - F((F(3) \times 9))) + ((0! + 5!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43907 &:= (((F(4))!) \times (3! + F((9 + 0!)))) - F(7) \\
 43910 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9))) - 10) \\
 43912 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(9) - (1 \times 2)))) \\
 43913 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (9 + ((-1 + 3!)!)) \\
 43914 &:= -(((F(4))! - ((3!)! \times (F((9 + 1)) + (F(4))!))) \\
 43915 &:= (((F(4))!) \times (3! + F((9 + 1)))) - (5) \\
 43916 &:= -(4) + ((3! + F((9 + 1))) \times 6!) \\
 43917 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(9) + 1))) - 7) \\
 43919 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9))) - (1^9)) \\
 \\
 43920 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 0 \\
 43921 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 1 \\
 43922 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 2 \\
 43923 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 3 \\
 43924 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 4 \\
 43925 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 5 \\
 43926 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 6 \\
 43927 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 7 \\
 43928 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 8 \\
 43929 &:= F(4)!! \times (3! + F(9 + F(2))) + 9 \\
 \\
 43931 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(9) + 3))) - 1) \\
 43932 &:= (((F((4! - 3!)) \times (-F(9))) - F(3!))/(-2)) \\
 43933 &:= (((F((F(4))!))!)/(-3!)) + ((F(9) + 3)^3) \\
 43934 &:= ((F((4! - 3!)) \times (F(9)/F(3))) + (F(4))!) \\
 43934 &:= ((F((4! - 3!)) \times (F(9)/F(3))) + (F(4))!) \\
 43935 &:= (((F(4))! + (F(3))!) + (9 + ((3!)! \times 5))) \\
 43936 &:= ((F((4! - 3!)) \times (F(9)/F(3))) + F(6)) \\
 43937 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(F(3!)) \times 9) - F(3)) \times F(7))) \\
 43938 &:= (F(4!) - (((3!)! \times (9 \times 3))/8)) \\
 43939 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((9 \times F(F(3!))) - F(9))) \\
 43940 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(9) + (4) + 0!))) \\
 43941 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + F(9)) \times (4 \times 1))) \\
 43942 &:= (((((F(4))! + F(F(F(3!)))) + F(9)) \times 4) - 2) \\
 43943 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (-9) + (F((F(4))!) \times F(F(3!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43944 &:= (F(4!) - (((3 \times F(9)) \times 4!) - 4!)) \\
 43945 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((3!)! + (9 - 4)) \times 5)) \\
 43946 &:= (F(4!) - ((-(F(3) - 9))^4 + F(F(6)))) \\
 43947 &:= (F(4) \times (((3^9) + (F(4)!)) - (7!))) \\
 43949 &:= (F(F((F(4)!)) + ((F((F(3) \times 9))/F(F(4))) \times F(9))) \\
 43950 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(F(3!)) + 9) \times (5! + 0!))) \\
 43952 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(9) \times 5) - 2)) \\
 43953 &:= ((4! + (F(3!))!) + (9 + (5 \times (3!)))) \\
 43954 &:= -(((F((4! - 3!)) + (F(9) \times (-5))) - F(4!))) \\
 43956 &:= ((F(F(4)) + (F(3!))!) + (F(9) + (5 \times 6!))) \\
 43957 &:= -(((F(F(F(4))) - (F(3!))!) - (F(9) \times (5! - F(7)))))) \\
 43958 &:= (4 + (((F(F(F(3!))) + F(9)) \times 5) - F(F(8)))) \\
 43959 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9))) + (5 + F(9))) \\
 43962 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F(F(3!)) - ((F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-2)))) \\
 43963 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((-((F(3!) + 9)) + F(F(F(6))))/3)) \\
 43964 &:= ((F(4!) - F((F(3) \times 9))) + (6!/4)) \\
 43965 &:= (F(4!) - ((3 \times 9) \times F((6 + 5)))) \\
 43966 &:= (F((4! - F(F(3)))) - (((-9) - 6!) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 43967 &:= (((((F(4)! \times F((3! + 9))) + (F(6)!)) - F(7)) \\
 43968 &:= ((4! \times (F((3 + 9)) + F(6))) + 8!) \\
 43971 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(9) + F(7)))) - 1) \\
 43972 &:= ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-3) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) - 2) \\
 43973 &:= (((((F(4)! \times F((3! + 9))) - 7) + (F(3!))!) \\
 43974 &:= (F(4!) - (F(3) - (9 - (7^4)))) \\
 43977 &:= -((((F(4)! - 3!!) - (9 \times (7! - F(F(7)))))) \\
 43979 &:= (-4!) + ((F(F(3!)) \times (9 \times F(F(7)))) - F(9)) \\
 \\
 43980 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 0 \\
 43981 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 1 \\
 43982 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 2 \\
 43983 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 3 \\
 43984 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 4 \\
 43985 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 5 \\
 43986 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 6 \\
 43987 &:= F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$43988 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 8$$

$$43989 := F(4)! \times F(9 + 3!) + 8! + 9$$

$$43991 := (((F(4))! + F(F(F(3!)))) - 9!)/(- (9 - 1))$$

$$43992 := (F(4!) - (F(3!) \times (9 \times (F(9) - F(2))))$$

$$43993 := (((F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (9! + 9))/F(3!))$$

$$43994 := (F(4!) + ((F(3) - (99 \times 4!)))$$

$$43998 := (F(F(4)) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - (9! + F(9)))/(-8))$$

$$44004 := ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + F((F((F(4)! + (0! + 0!)))) \times 4)$$

$$44013 := ((4 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!))) - 0!)) + (F(13)))$$

$$44016 := ((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (- (0!) + F(F((1 + 6))))$$

$$44017 := ((4 \times F(F((4 \times (0! + 1)))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$44018 := ((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (0! + F(F(-(1 - 8))))$$

$$44024 := ((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (((0! + 2)!)/F(4)))$$

$$44025 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F((F(4)!)) + (((0! + 2)!)) \times 5))$$

$$44030 := (((F(4))!^4 - 0!) \times F((F(3!) + 0!))$$

$$44035 := ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-(4! - 0!) - 3!) \times (-5)))$$

$$44036 := (4 \times ((F(4) \times F(F((03!))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$44037 := (((4^{F(4)} - 0!) \times 3) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$44038 := (F(4!) - (F(F(((F(4)! + 0!))) \times (F(3) + 8)))$$

$$44039 := (F(F(4)) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (F(F((0! + 3!))) \times 9)))$$

$$44042 := ((F(F((F(4)!)) + 40) \times (((F(4)!))! + 2))$$

$$44043 := (((F(4))!^4 \times F((0! + F((F(4)!)))) - (F(F(3!))))$$

$$44044 := (((4^{F(4)} + 0!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 4)$$

$$44045 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((F(4)!))! + (0! + 4!)) \times 5))$$

$$44046 := (((4! \times 4!) + F((- (0!) + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 6)$$

$$44048 := (((4 \times 4) \times F(F((0! + (F(4)!)))) + 8!)$$

$$44057 := ((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (F(F((0! + (5)))) \times F(7)))$$

$$44058 := (F(4!) - ((F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!) \times (5 \times F(8))))$$

$$44062 := (((F(4))!^4 \times F((0! + F(6)))) - 2)$$

$$44063 := (((F(4))!^4 \times F((0! + F(6)))) - F(F(3)))$$

$$44066 := ((F(F(4)) \times ((4! - 0!) \times 6!)) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$44068 := (- (F(4!)) - (4 \times (F((0! + F(F(6)))) - 8!))$$

$$44072 := ((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (F(-(0! - F(7)))) \times 2))$$

$$44078 := ((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((0! + F(7)) \times F(8)))$$

- 44079** := $(F(F((F(4)!))) \times (F(F(4)) + ((0 - F(F(7))) \times (-9))))$
- 44084** := $((F(4) \times (4! + 0!)) + F(F(8))) \times 4$
- 44092** := $-((F((F(4)!)) - (((F(4)! \times (0! + F(9)))^2)))$
- 44094** := $(((((F(4))!^4) + 0!) \times F(9)) - 4)$
- 44095** := $((F((F(4)!))! + (((F(4)!))! + (0! + F(9))) \times 5))$
- 44096** := $-((4^{F(4)+0!}) - (9!/6))$
- 44098** := $(((((F(4))!^4) + 0!) \times F((9!/8!)))$
- 44099** := $((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((0! + F(9)) \times (-9)))$
- 44100** := $((F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 100)$
- 44102** := $(F(F(4)) + ((F(F((F(4)!))) \times 10)^2))$
- 44103** := $((F(4) + ((F(4)!))! \times (F(10) + 3!))$
- 44104** := $(4 + ((F(F((F(4)!))) \times 10)^{F(F(4))}))$
- 44106** := $(F(4!) + (F((4 + 10)) \times (-6)))$
- 44107** := $(F(4!) - ((F(F((F(4)!)))! / ((10!) \times (F(7)!)))$
- 44109** := $((-(((F(4)!))! - F((F(F((F(4)!)) - (1 + 0!)))) \times (-9))$
- 44113** := $((F(4!)/F(4)) + F((-1 + ((1 + 3)!)))$
- 44114** := $((F(4!)/F(4)) + 1) + F((-1 + 4!))$
- 44116** := $(4 \times (-(((F(4)! - (F(11)))) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 44124** := $(((-F(4!)) + ((F(4)!))! / (-12)) + (F((F(4)!))!))$
- 44127** := $((4 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(12))) - F(F(7)))$
- 44128** := $(F(4!) - ((F((F(4)!))! / (F(12)/8)))$
- 44133** := $(F(4!) - (((4! + 1) + 3!) \times 3))$
- 44134** := $((F(F((F(4)!)) + F(4!)) - (F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) / F(4)))$
- 44135** := $(((((F(4))!^{F(4)!}) - 1) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-5!)))$
- 44136** := $(F(4!) - (F(4) \times (((1 + 3)! + 6!)))$
- 44137** := $((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (((-1 + 3!)! + F(F(7))))$
- 44140** := $((F(4!)/F(F((F(4)!))) - 1) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - 0!))$
- 44143** := $(F(4!) - ((4! + 1) \times F((F(4) + F(3!))))$
- 44144** := $((F(F((F(4)!)) + 41) \times (((F(4)!))! - F((F(4)!))))$
- 44144** := $((F(F((F(4)!)) + 41) \times (((F(4)!))! - F((F(4)!))))$
- 44145** := $((4 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (1 + (F(4) \times 5!)))$
- 44147** := $((-F(4!)) / F(F(((4 - 1)!))) + ((F(4!) - F(7)))$
- 44148** := $(F(4!) - (F(4) \times ((-1 + ((F(4)!))! + (F(8))))$
- 44153** := $((F((F(4)!))! + F(F(((F(4)! + 1)))) + (5 \times (3)!))$

- 44154** := $(F(4!) - (41 \times 54))$
44155 := $(F(4!) - ((F(4!)/F(F((1+5)))) + (5)))$
44156 := $((F(4!) - 4) - (F((-((1-5))))/F(F(6))))$
44157 := $((F(4!) - (4!)) - (F(-((1-5))))^7)$
44158 := $((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - (F((-((1-5))))/F(8)))$
44159 := $((-F(4!))/F(F(F(4)!))) - (1 - F((-((5-9))))))$
- 44160** := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 0$
44161 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 1$
44162 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 2$
44163 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 3$
44164 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 4$
44165 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 5$
44166 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 6$
44167 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 7$
44168 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 8$
44169 := $F(4!) - F(4!)/F(F(1 \times 6)) + 9$
- 44173** := $(F(4!) + ((F((4-1)) - (F(7)^3)))$
44174 := $(F(4!) - (-((4-1)) + (F(7)^{F(4)})))$
44176 := $(F(4!) - ((41 + F(F(7))) \times F(6)))$
44177 := $((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(4!)/(-1 + F(7))) - 7))$
44178 := $-(((F(4)! - ((F(4!)/(-1 + F(7))) + 8!)))$
44180 := $(F(4!) - ((F(4)^{-1+8}) + 0!))$
44181 := $(F(4!) - ((4-1)^{8-1}))$
44182 := $(F(4!) - ((F(4)^{-1+8}) - F(2)))$
44183 := $(F(4!) - ((F(4)^{-1+8}) - F(3)))$
44184 := $(F(4!) - ((F(4)^{-1+8}) - F(4)))$
44185 := $((F(4!) + (F(4)!)) - ((1 - F(F(8)))/(-5)))$
44194 := $((-F(4!))/F(F(((4-1)!))) - (-F(9) - F(4!)))$
44195 := $((F((F(4)!))!) + (((F(4)! + F((1+9))) \times 5))$
44196 := $((((F(4)! - ((4+1)!)) \times (-F(9))) + (F(6)!))$
44202 := $(F(4!) - (((F(4)! + 2) \times (0! + 2)))$
44204 := $(F(4!) - ((F(4) \times ((2+0!)!) + 4))$
44205 := $(F(4!) - (F(4) \times (F(2) + ((0! + (5!))!)))$

- 44206 := ((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - ((2 + 0!) × 6!))
- 44208 := (((F(4))!⁴) × (2 + 0!)) + 8!
- 44211 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × (((2 + 1))!)! - 1))
- 44214 := (F(4!) - ((F(4) × (((2 + 1))!)! - (F(4))!))
- 44216 := (F(4!) - ((F(4) × (((2 + 1))!)! - F(6)))
- 44224 := (F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F(F(4)! + F(2))))² - F(4)!!
- 44225 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) - (F((4! - 2))))/(-2)) × 5)
- 44226 := (F(4!) - (-F(4) × ((F((2 + 2))!)! - (6!))))
- 44232 := (F(4!) - (4! × F((2 + (3²))))))
- 44233 := ((F(4!) + (4! + F(2))) - (3 × (3!)!))
- 44234 := ((F(4!) + (4! + 2)) - ((3!)! × F(4)))
- 44235 := -((F(F((F(4))!)) - (4 × ((-2) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5!)))
- 44236 := ((4 × (F(4²)) - F(3!)) + (F(6))!)
- 44237 := ((4 × (F((F((F(4))!) + 2)) + F(F(F(3!)))))) + F(F(7)))
- 44238 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × ((-2) + 3!! - 8)))
- 44239 := (F(4!) - ((F(4) × (F(2) + 3!!)) - F(9)))
- 44243 := -((F(F((F(4))!)) - (4 × (((F(2) + (4))!)! + F(F(F(3!)))))))
- 44244 := (((((F(4))!)! - (4!/2)) × (-F(4))) + F(4!))
- 44244 := (((((F(4))!)! - (4!/2)) × (-F(4))) + F(4!))
- 44246 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) × (4! - 2)) + (4 × F(F(F(6))))))
- 44247 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × (((2 + 4))! - F(7))))
- 44248 := (4 × ((-4) + ((F(2) + (4))!)! + F(F(8))))
- 44252 := (F(4!) - ((F(F((F(4))!)) + 25)²))
- 44253 := (((F(4))! + (F(F((F(4))!))²)) × (5! - F(F(3!))))
- 44254 := (((-F(4!))/F(F((F(4))!))) × (-25)) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))
- 44255 := ((4 × (F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (F(2) - 5!)) - (5))
- 44256 := (F(4!) - ((4! - (-2) × 5!) × F(6)))
- 44257 := ((4 × (F(F((4 × 2))) + 5!)) - 7)
- 44258 := (F(F(4)) + (4 × ((-2) + 5! + F(F(8))))))
- 44259 := (F(4!) - ((F(F((F(4))!)) - 2) × (5! - 9)))
- 44260 := (4 × (((F(4) + 2))! + F(F(F(6)))) - 0!)
- 44262 := ((4 × (((F(4) + 2))! + F(F(F(6)))))) - 2)
- 44263 := ((4 × (((F(4) + 2))! + F(F(F(6)))))) - F(F(3)))
- 44264 := (((4 × F(4²)) + (F(6))!) - 4)
- 44265 := (F(F(F(4))) + (4 × (F(F((2 + 6))) + 5!)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 44266 &:= -((F(F(4)) - ((4 \times F((2 \times F(6)))) + (F(6))!)) \\
 44267 &:= ((F(4!) - 4) - ((F(2) + F(6)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 44268 &:= ((4 \times F((4 + (2 \times 6)))) + 8!) \\
 44269 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - (F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \times 9)) \\
 44270 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4)^2) \times F(F(7))) + 0!)) \\
 44271 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(4)^2) \times F(F((7 \times 1)))) \\
 44272 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4)^2) \times F(F(7))) - F(2))) \\
 44273 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4)^2) \times F(F(7))) - F(3))) \\
 44274 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4)^2) \times F(F(7))) - F(4))) \\
 44275 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times 4!) - 2) \times F(F(7))) + (5)) \\
 44276 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times 4!) - 2) \times F(F(7))) + 6) \\
 44277 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(4))!) - ((2 + 7) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 44278 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times 4!) - 2) \times F(F(7))) + 8) \\
 44279 &:= ((F(4!) + (4 \times 2)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-9))) \\
 44283 &:= (((F(4) \times F(F((F(4))!)))^2) + ((8! - 3!)) \\
 44284 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((4 + F((2 \times 8))) \times 4)) \\
 44285 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) + (4 \times (F((F(2) \times F(8))) + 5!))) \\
 44286 &:= (((F(4))! + ((F(4))!)) \times (F((2 + 8)) + (6))) \\
 44288 &:= (F(4!) - ((4 + (2^8)) \times 8)) \\
 44289 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F((4 \times 2)) \times F(8)) \times 9)) \\
 44290 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((F(F((F(4))!))^2) \times 9) + 0!)) \\
 44293 &:= (4 + (((F(F((F(4))!))^2) \times 9) + (F(3))!)) \\
 44294 &:= (((-F(4)) + (F((F(4))!))^2) \times (-F(9))) + F(4!)) \\
 44295 &:= ((4! - (F((4^2)) \times 9)) \times (-5)) \\
 44296 &:= (F(4!) - (4 \times ((2^9) + 6))) \\
 44297 &:= (((F(4))!^4) \times (F(2) \times F(9))) + F(F(7)) \\
 44304 &:= (F(4!) - (((F((F(4))!))! / 30) + (((F(4))!))!)) \\
 44310 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(4))! \times ((3!)! - (F(10)))) \\
 44316 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4))!))! + (F(3))!) / (-1 + F(F(6)))) \\
 \\
 44320 &:= F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 0 \\
 44321 &:= F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 1 \\
 44322 &:= F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 2 \\
 44323 &:= F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 3 \\
 44324 &:= F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$44325 := F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 5$$

$$44326 := F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 6$$

$$44327 := F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 7$$

$$44328 := F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 8$$

$$44329 := F(4!) - 4^{3!} / 2 + 9$$

$$44331 := ((F(4!) - F(F((F(4)!))) - ((F(3!))! / (F(F(3!)) - 1))))$$

$$44333 := (((F((F(4)!))! - (F((F(4)!)) \times F(F(3!)))) + F((-F(3) + F(F(3!))))))$$

$$44334 := ((((((F(4)!)/F(F(4))) - F(F(3!))) \times (-3!)) + F(4!))$$

$$44336 := (((F(4)!)^4 + F(3!)) \times F((3 + 6)))$$

$$44337 := ((F(4!) + F(F(F(4)))) - (F(3!) \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(7)))))$$

$$44338 := ((4 \times ((4^3) - 3)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$44339 := (((F(4)!)^{F(4)!} - 3!) - F((F(3!) + 9)))$$

$$44340 := (4 \times (((F(4)! \times (3!)) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 0!))))$$

$$44342 := (F(4!) - (((4! + F(F(3!)))^{F(F(4))} + F(2)))$$

$$44343 := (F(4!) - (((4! - 3) + 4!)^{F(3)}))$$

$$44344 := (((F(4) + (4))!) + (34^{F(4)}))$$

$$44344 := (((F(4) + (4))!) + (34^{F(4)}))$$

$$44345 := (F(4!) - ((4 - F(F(3!))) \times (F(F(F(4))) - 5!)))$$

$$44346 := ((F(4!) - (F(4)!)) - ((3!^4) + 6!))$$

$$44347 := (F(4!) - (43 \times 47))$$

$$44348 := (((4!^4) / 3!) - F(F(4))) - F(F(8)))$$

$$44349 := -(((F((4! + (4))) + ((F(3) + (4))!) - 9!))$$

$$44350 := (((4!^4) / 3!) - F(F(F((5 + 0!))))$$

$$44351 := (F(4!) - (((F(4)! \times (F(3!))!) / 5!) + 1))$$

$$44352 := (F(4!) - (((4 + 3)! / (-5)) \times (-2)))$$

$$44353 := (F(F(F(4))) - ((F(4!) - ((3!) \times (5! + 3!))))$$

$$44354 := ((F(4!) / 4) + ((F(3!)^5) - (F(4)!))$$

$$44355 := ((F(4!) / 4) + ((F(3!)^5) - (5)))$$

$$44356 := ((4 - F(4!)) + (((3! + 5!) \times 6!))$$

$$44357 := (((F((F(4)!))! + F((-F(F(4))) + F(F(3!)))) - F((5 + 7)))$$

$$44358 := (F(4) \times (((4 \times F(3!)) \times 5!) + F(F(8))))$$

$$44360 := ((F(4!) / 4) + (F(3!)^{6-0!}))$$

$$44364 := (((F(4)! \times (F(F(4)) + ((3!) \times F(F(6)))) - F(4!))$$

- 44365 := (((F((F(4)))!)^{F(4)!}) + (F(F(3)) - (F(6))!)) / 5)
- 44366 := (-F(F(4))) + (((4!)! / 3) / (F(F(6))!) + (F(6))!))
- 44367 := ((-((F((4 × 4)) + 3!)) + (F(6))!) + (7!))
- 44368 := ((4^{F(4)!}) - ((3! × F(6)) - 8!))
- 44370 := -((F(4!) - ((4! - 3!) × (7! + 0!))))
- 44371 := ((4 × (F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F(F(3!)) × 7))) - 1)
- 44372 := ((-F((4 × 4))) + (F(3!))!) + ((7! - F(2)))
- 44373 := -((F((4 × 4)) - ((3 × 7!) × 3))
- 44374 := (((4^{F(4)!}) + (F(3!))!) - (7 × (F(4))!))
- 44375 := ((F((F(4))!))! - (((F(4))! - F((3! + F(7)))) + 5!))
- 44376 := ((4! - F(4!)) + ((3 × 7!) × 6))
- 44377 := (F(4!) - ((F(4) × (3!))! - ((F(7) × F(7)))))
- 44378 := ((4 × ((4!)³) + (7)) - F(F(8)))
- 44379 := -(((F((4 × 4)) - 3!) - (7! × 9))
- 44382 := (F(4!) - (F(F(4)) × (3! + F((8 × 2)))))
- 44384 := (((4^{F(4)!}) - F(3!)) + ((8! - 4!))
- 44385 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((4 + F(-((F(3) - F(8))))) - 5!))
- 44387 := (F(4!) - ((F(F(4)) × F((F(3) × 8))) + 7))
- 44388 := ((F(4!) - (F(4))!) - ((F(3) × F((8 + 8)))))
- 44392 := (-((4! - (4^{3!}))) + ((9 - F(2))!))
- 44393 := -((((F(4!) / (F(4))!) + F(3!)) - 9!) / F(3!))
- 44394 := (F(4!) - ((4! - 3) × 94))
- 44396 := (F(F(4)) + (((F(4!) / (-3!)) + 9!) / F(6)))
- 44397 := (F(4!) + ((F(4) - (F(3) × F((9 + 7)))))
- 44398 := ((4^{F(4)!}) + ((F(3) × (-9)) + 8!))
- 44403 := (((4^{F(4)!}) - F(((F(4))! + 0!))) + (F(3!))!)
- 44404 := (((F(4))! + ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (4! + 0!)) × 4))
- 44406 := (((F(4)^{F(F(4)!)}) × (F(4))!) + ((0! + (6))!))
- 44407 := (((F(4)^{F(F(4)!)}) × (F(4))!) + (0! + 7!))
- 44408 := (((F(4))! + (4 × (-4!) + F(F(08)))))
- 44412 := (((4^{F(4)!}) - 4) + (F(((1 + 2))!))!)
- 44413 := (((4^{F(4)!}) - F(4)) + (F(((1 × 3))!))!)
- 44414 := (((4^{F(4)!}) + (F(((4 - 1))!))! - F(F(4)))
- 44417 := (F(F(F(4))) + ((4^{F(4)!}) + ((1 + 7))!))

$$\begin{aligned} 44418 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((4^{(4-1)!}) + 8!)) \\ 44419 &:= (((4^{F(4)!}) + F(4)) + (-((1-9)))!) \\ 44420 &:= ((F((F(4)!)))! - (-4) - (4^{(2+0)!})) \\ 44422 &:= ((F((F(4)!)))! + (((4^{F(4)!}) + (F((2+2))))!)) \\ 44423 &:= (((F(4!)/(-4!)) + F(4!)) - F((F(2)+3!))) \\ 44424 &:= -(((F(4)^4) \times 4!) - F(24)) \\ 44426 &:= (F(4!) - ((44^2) + 6)) \\ 44427 &:= (((F(4!)/(-4!)) + F(4!)) - (2+7)) \\ 44428 &:= ((4^{F(4)!}) - ((4!/(-2)) - 8!)) \\ 44429 &:= (((F(4!)/(-4!)) + F(4!)) + ((2-9))) \\ \\ 44430 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 0 \\ 44431 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 1 \\ 44432 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 2 \\ 44433 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 3 \\ 44434 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 4 \\ 44435 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 5 \\ 44436 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 6 \\ 44437 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 7 \\ 44438 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 8 \\ 44439 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) - 3! + 9 \\ \\ 44440 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 0 \\ 44441 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 1 \\ 44442 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 2 \\ 44443 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 3 \\ 44444 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 4 \\ 44445 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 5 \\ 44446 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 6 \\ 44447 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 7 \\ 44448 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 8 \\ 44449 &:= -F(4!)/4! + F(4!) + 4 + 9 \\ \\ 44450 &:= (F(4!) - (F(F(4)) \times ((F((F(4)!)) \times 5!) - 0!))) \\ 44451 &:= ((F((F(4)!)))! + ((F(4)^4) \times 51)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44452 &:= (F(4!) - (-4) \times ((-4) \times 5!) + F(2))) \\
 44453 &:= (((-((4! + 4!)) + F((4! - (5)))) + (F(3!))!) \\
 44454 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(4))!) + ((-4) \times 5!) \times 4) \\
 44456 &:= (F(4!) - (((4 \times 4) \times 5!) - F(6))) \\
 44457 &:= (F(4!) - (((4! + F(4)) + 5!) \times F(7))) \\
 44458 &:= (((((F(4))!)! + (4!)) + ((F((F(4))!)^5) + F(F(8)))) \\
 44459 &:= -(((F((4! + (4))) + F((F(4) \times 5))) - 9!)) \\
 44460 &:= (((F(4))!)! + ((F(4)^{F(4)!}) \times 60)) \\
 44461 &:= -((F((F(4))!) - ((F(4)^{F(4)!}) \times 61))) \\
 44462 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(F((F(4) + (4)))) + (6!)) \times 2)) \\
 44463 &:= (((((F(4!)/(-4!)) + F(4!)) + F(F(6))) + 3!) \\
 44464 &:= (F(4!) - (-((4^4)) + (6! \times F(4)))) \\
 44466 &:= (((F(4) \times (F(4))!) + F(4!)) - ((F(6))!/F(F(6)))) \\
 44467 &:= ((-4!) + ((F(4))!)!) + ((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(7)) \\
 44468 &:= ((F(4!) + (4! - (4))) - ((F(6))!/F(8))) \\
 44469 &:= (((4^{F(4)}) - F(4)) \times (6! + 9)) \\
 44470 &:= (((F(4))!^{F(4)!}) - ((F(4)^7) - 0!)) \\
 44471 &:= (F(4!) - ((F((F(4))!) \times (4 + F(F(7)))) + 1)) \\
 44472 &:= (F(4!) - (4 \times ((4 + F(F(7))) \times 2))) \\
 44473 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) + ((-4) - F(F(7))) \times F(3!))) \\
 44474 &:= (F(4!) - (((((F(4))!)! - (((F(4))! - F(F(7)))) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 44475 &:= (((F(4!) - ((F(4))!)!) - F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(7)) \times 5)) \\
 44476 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - (((F(4) \times 7!)/F(6)))) \\
 44477 &:= ((F((F(4))!)!) + (-4!) + F(((-(4 - 7))! + F(7)))) \\
 44478 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4))!/F(F(4))) \times (7!/8))) \\
 44479 &:= ((F(4!) - F((F(4))!)) - ((-4!) + F(F(7))) \times 9)) \\
 \\
 44480 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 0 \\
 44481 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 1 \\
 44482 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 2 \\
 44483 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 3 \\
 44484 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 4 \\
 44485 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 5 \\
 44486 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 6 \\
 44487 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44488 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 8 \\
 44489 &:= F(4)!! + 4 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 9 \\
 44491 &:= (((F(4!)/(-4!)) + F(4!)) + F((9 + 1))) \\
 44492 &:= ((F(4!) - ((4!/4)!) - (F(9)^2)) \\
 44493 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) - ((F(4))!)) + ((F(4!) - (F(9)^{F(3)}))) \\
 44494 &:= (((F(4!)/(-4!)) + F(4!)) + (F(9) + 4!)) \\
 44495 &:= (F((F(F((F(4)!)) - F(F(4)))) - ((F(4))! - (F((F((9 - 5))!))!))) \\
 44496 &:= (4! \times (4! + (F(4) \times F((9 + 6)))) \\
 44497 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) - (F((F(4) + 9)) \times F(7)))) \\
 44498 &:= ((F(4!) - (F(4))!) + (F((4 + 9)) \times (-8))) \\
 44499 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(F(4)))) - (F(-((4! - F(9)))) \times F(9))) \\
 44500 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - ((F((4! - 5))) - 0!) \times (-0!)) \\
 44501 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(((4 \times 5) - 01)))) \\
 44502 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((4! - 5))) + ((0 \times 2)!)) \\
 44503 &:= ((4 \times F(F((F(4) + 5)))) - (0! - 3!)) \\
 44504 &:= (((F(4))! + (F(4!) - F((5 + 0!) \times F(4)))) \\
 44505 &:= ((4 + F((4! - 5))) + (F((0! + 5)))!) \\
 44506 &:= (((4 + F((4! - 5))) + 0!) + (F(6))!) \\
 44507 &:= (((F(4))! + F((4! - 5))) + ((0! + 7)))! \\
 44508 &:= (((F(4))! + F((4! - 5))) + (0! + 8!)) \\
 44509 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) + F((4! - 5))) + (-((0! - 9)))!) \\
 44512 &:= (((F(4))! + (4 \times (F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + 2))) \\
 44513 &:= ((F(4)^{F(4)!}) + ((5 - 1) \times F(F(F(3)))) \\
 44514 &:= ((-((F(4))!) - ((F(4))!)) + (5! \times F(14))) \\
 44515 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (((F(4))! + ((5! - 1))) \times 5)) \\
 44516 &:= ((4 \times (F(4) + F(F(F((5 + 1)))))) + (6!)) \\
 44517 &:= ((-F(4) - ((F(4))!)) + (5! \times F((1 + F(7)))) \\
 44519 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! - ((F(F(F(4))) - (5! \times (1 + F(9)))))) \\
 44520 &:= (((((F(4))!^{F(4)} - (5)^2) - 0!) \\
 44521 &:= (((((F(4))!^{F(4)} - (5)^2) \times 1) \\
 44522 &:= (((((F(4))!^{F(4)} - (5)^2) + F(2)) \\
 44523 &:= (((((F(4))!^{F(4)} - (5)^2) + F(3)) \\
 44524 &:= (((((F(4))!^{F(4)} - (5)^2) + F(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 44525 := ((4! + F((4! - (5)))) + (F((F(2) + (5))))!)
44526 := (((4! + F((4! - (5)))) + F(2)) + (F(6)))!
44527 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F((4! - (5))) + (2 × F(7))))
44528 := (((F(4!)/(F(4)!)) × (-5! + F(2)))/(-F(8)))
44530 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) × (-5))/(-F((3! + 0!))))))
44532 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × (F((5 × 3)) + 2)))
44533 := (((4^{F(4)!)} + ((5! - 3))) + (F(3!)))!
44534 := (F(4!) - ((F(4) × F((5 × 3))) + (4)))
44535 := (F(4!) - (F((F(F(4)) + (5))) × (F(F(3!)) + 5!)))
44536 := (((4^{F(4)!)} + 5!) + ((F(3) + (6)))!)
44537 := ((F(4!) + F(F(4))) - ((5! + F(F(3!))) × F(7)))
44538 := (F(4!) - ((4! × F((5 × 3)))/8))
44539 := (((4 + F((4! - (5)))) + (F(3!)))! + F(9))
44541 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × (F((5 × F(4))) - 1)))
44543 := (F(4!) - ((4 + F(F((5 + F(4)))))/3!))
44545 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((F(4)! + (5^{F(4)})) × 5))
44546 := (((-F(4)) × F((F(4) × 5))) + F(4!)) + F(6))
44547 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × ((-5!) + ((F(4)!))! + 7)))
44548 := (((F(4!)/(-4!)) + 5!) + F(4!)) - 8
44549 := (((F((F(4)!))!) - F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((5^{F(4)}) × F(9)))
44553 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × (-5 + F((5 × 3))))))
44554 := (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (((F((F(4)!))⁵) + 5!) + ((F(4)!))!))
44556 := (F((F(F((F(4)!)) - F(F(4)))) - (-55) - (F(6)!))
44559 := (F(4!) - (((F(4) × 5) × 5!) + 9))
44562 := (F(4!) + ((F(4) × ((5! - 6!) - 2))))
44563 := (F(4!) - (((4 - 5!) + F(F(F(6))))/3!))
44564 := (F(4!) - (4 - ((5! - 6!) × F(4))))
44565 := (F(4!) - (F(4) + ((5!/F(6)) × 5!)))
44566 := ((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - ((5! × F(F(6))) - (6!)))
44567 := ((F(4!) - F(F(F(4)))) - (5! × (F(6) + (7))))
44568 := (F(4!) - (((4 × 5) × 6!)/8))
44569 := (F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) + (5! × (-6 + 9))))
44572 := (F(4!) - (-4 + (5! × (F(7) + 2))))
44573 := (((F(4)!))! + (F(4!) - (-5 + (7!/F(3))))))

- 44574 := ((F(4!) + (F(4))!) - (5! + (7!/F(4))))
- 44575 := ((F(4!) - F(F((F(F(4)) + (5)))))) - (F(7) × 5!))
- 44576 := (((F(F(4)) - F((F(4) × 5))) × (-7)) + (F(6))!)
- 44577 := ((4! + F(4)) × ((5! + (7)) × F(7)))
- 44583 := (F(4!) - ((F(F(F(4))) - 5!) × (-F(8) - 3!)))
- 44584 := (F(4!) - (4 × (5 + (F(8)^{F(F(4))})))
- 44586 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × ((5! - F(8)) × 6)))
- 44587 := (F(4!) - (((-4) + 5!) + F(8)) × F(7)))
- 44588 := (((F(4))!)! + ((F(F(F(4))) - (5)) × (-F(8)) - F(F(8))))
- 44589 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) - (-4) × 5!) × 89)
- 44590 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(F(4)) + 5!) × (F(9) + 0!)))
- 44592 := (F(4!) - (F(4) × 592))
- 44595 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (45 × 95))
- 44596 := -((F((F(4))!) - (((F(4))! + 5!) × F(9)) + (F(6))!))
- 44597 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((F(4))! + 5!) × F(9)) - 7))
- 44598 := -(((F(4))! - (((F(4))! + 5!) × F(9)) + 8!))
- 44603 := (-(((F(4))! × ((F(4))! - (6!)) + 0!)) + (F(3!))!)
- 44604 := (F(4!) - ((F(F(4)) × F(F(6)))^{F(F(04))}))
- 44606 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))! - (F((F(6) + 0!)) - (F(6))!))
- 44608 := (F((F(4))!) × ((4! - 6!) - 0!) × (-8))
- 44613 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((F(4))! × (6! - 1)) - F(F(3!))))
- 44616 := (((F(4))! × (-4) + 6!)) + (F((1 × 6))!)
- 44617 := ((-4!) - ((F(4))!))! + ((F(6))! + (1 + 7!))
- 44618 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))! + ((F(6))! - (1 + F(8))))
- 44619 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))! - (F(F(6)) - (-((1 - 9))!))
- 44620 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))! + (((F(6))! - (20))))
- 44622 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(4))! × (6! - F((2 + 2))))
- 44623 := (((F(4))! × (-F(4) - 6!)) + F(2)) + (F(3!))!)
- 44624 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))! + (((F(6))! - (2⁴))))
- 44625 := ((-F(F(4))) + F(((F(4))! + F(6)))) × (-F(2) - 5!))
- 44626 := -((F(F(4)) - (((F(4))! × (6! - 2)) + (F(6))!))
- 44627 := (((4!/4))! × 62) - F(7))
- 44629 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))! + (((F(6))! - (2 + 9))))
- 44630 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (-4) + (6 × ((3!)! - 0!)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 44631 &:= -((((F(4)^{F(4)!}) - (F(6))!) - ((3! + 1)!)) \\
 44632 &:= (((F(4))! \times ((F(4))!)!) - (F(6) - (F((3 \times 2))))!) \\
 44633 &:= (((-4) - F(4)) + (F(6))!) + (3! \times (3!)!) \\
 44634 &:= ((F(4)!) - (F(4))!) - (((6 \times F(3))^{F(4)})) \\
 44636 &:= (F(4)!) - (4 - (-((6^3)) \times F(6))) \\
 44638 &:= (((4!/4) \times 6!) - F(3)) + 8! \\
 44639 &:= (((F(4))! \times ((F(4))!)!) + (((F(6))! + F(3!)) - 9)) \\
 \\
 44640 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 0 \\
 44641 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 1 \\
 44642 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 2 \\
 44643 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 3 \\
 44644 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 4 \\
 44645 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 5 \\
 44646 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 6 \\
 44647 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 7 \\
 44648 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 8 \\
 44649 &:= F(4!) - (4 + F(6))^{F(4)} + 9 \\
 \\
 44650 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((-4) + F(F(6)))) - ((5! + 0!)) \\
 44651 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((-4) + F(F(6)))) + (5! \times (-1)) \\
 44652 &:= (F(4) \times ((-(4 - 6) + 5!)^2)) \\
 44653 &:= (((F(4))! \times ((F(4))!)!) + (((F(6))! + F((5 + F(3)))))) \\
 44654 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((-4) + F(F(6)))) - (5! - F(4)) \\
 44655 &:= (F(4) \times ((F((4 + F(F(6))))/5) - 5!)) \\
 44656 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((4! - F(6)))) + (-5 - 6!) \\
 44657 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((F(4))! \times (6! + 5)) - F(7))) \\
 44658 &:= ((F(4)!) - ((F(4) + 6!)) - F((-5) + F(8))) \\
 44659 &:= (((F((F(4))!))!)/(-4) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-5)) - 9)) \\
 44660 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((4! - F(6)))) - ((6! + 0!)) \\
 44661 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((4! - F(6)))) + (6! \times (-1)) \\
 44662 &:= ((4! - F(F(4))) - (6! \times (-62))) \\
 44663 &:= ((F(4)!) - F((4! - F(6)))) - (6! - F(3)) \\
 44665 &:= ((F(4)!) + (4 - 6!)) - F((F(F(6)) - (5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 44666** := (((F(F(4)) + (4!)) + (F(6))!) - (6! × (-6)))
44667 := (((4! + F(4)) + (F(6))!) - (6! - 7!))
44671 := (F(4!) - ((F((F(4))!) × (-F(F(6)) - F(F(7)))) + 1))
44672 := (F(4!) - (4 × ((F(F(6)) - F(F(7))) × (-2))))
44673 := (((F(4!) + (F(4))!) - F(F(6))) - (7!/3))
44674 := ((F(4!) - (F(4))!) - ((F(6) + (7!/F(4))))
44675 := (((F(4))! × ((F(4))!)!) + (((F(6))! + (7 × 5))))
44676 := (((F(4))!^{F(F(4))}) + (F(6))!) + ((7! - 6!))
44677 := ((F(4!) - 4) - ((F(6) + F(F(7))) × 7))
44678 := (-4) + (((F(4))! × (6! + 7)) + 8!)
44679 := ((-4!) × (F(F(4)) + (-F(6) × F(F(7)))) - 9)
44680 := ((F(4!) - F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(6)) × (-80)))
44681 := (F(4!) - (((F((F(4))!)!)/F(F(6))) - (F(F((8 - 1))))))
44682 := (((F(4))!^{F(4)!}) - (F((F(6) + 8)) × 2))
44683 := ((F((4 × (F(4))!)) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(8)³))
44684 := ((-4) + F(4 × 6)) - (8!/4!)
44685 := (F(4!) - (F(4) - (-((6 + 8)) × 5!))
44686 := (((F(4))! × (F(4)⁶)) + ((8! - F(6))))
44687 := (((F(4))! × (F(4)⁶)) + ((8! - 7)))
44689 := (F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) + ((6! × F(8))/(-9)))
44692 := (4 × ((-((F(4))!) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F((9 - 2))))))
44693 := (((F(4))!)! + (4 × F(F(F(6)))) + (9 × F(F(3))))
44694 := (((4 + 4))! + (6 × (9^{F(4)})))
44695 := (((F((F(4))!)!)/(-4)) - ((F(F(F(6))) + 9) × (-5)))
44696 := (F(F(4)) + (((F(4))! × (6! + 9)) + (F(6))!))
44697 := (F(4!) - (((F((F(4))!)!)/6) + (-9 - 7!))
44698 := (((F(4))! × (4 + 6!)) + ((F(9) + 8!))
44699 := -((F(F((F(4))!)) - (((F(4))!)! - (((F(6))! + 9!)))/(-9)))
44703 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (((F(4))!)! - F(F(7))) × (0! + F(3!)))
44704 := (F((F(4))!) × ((4! × F(F(7))) - 04))
44706 := ((-4!) × ((F((F(4))!) × (-F(F(7)))) + 0!)) - 6
44707 := ((4 × (F(F(F((F(4))!))) + ((F(F(7)) + 0!)))) - F(7))
44708 := (4 × (((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) × (-0!)) + F(F(8))))
44709 := ((F((F(4))!)! + ((-4!) + F(F(7))) × F(-((0! - 9))))

$$44711 := ((-4!) \times ((F((F(4)))! \times (-F(F(7)))) + 1)) - 1$$

$$44712 := (F(4!) - (4! \times (71 - 2)))$$

$$44713 := (F(4!) - (4! + (7 \times F(13))))$$

$$44714 := (F(F(4)) + (((F((F(4)))! \times F(F(7))) - 1) \times 4!))$$

$$44715 := (((F((F(4)))! \times (4! \times F(F(7)))) - F(F((1 + 5))))$$

$$44716 := ((-4) \times F((4! - (7)))) \times (-(1 + 6))$$

$$44717 := (F(4!) - (((F(F(4)))^7) - 1) \times F(7))$$

$$44719 := ((F((F(4)))! \times ((4! \times F(F(7))) - 1)) - 9)$$

$$44720 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 0$$

$$44721 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 1$$

$$44722 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 2$$

$$44723 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 3$$

$$44724 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 4$$

$$44725 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 5$$

$$44726 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 6$$

$$44727 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 7$$

$$44728 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 8$$

$$44729 := F(F(4)!) \times (4! \times F(F(7)) - 2) + 9$$

$$44730 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 0$$

$$44731 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 1$$

$$44732 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 2$$

$$44733 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 3$$

$$44734 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 4$$

$$44735 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 5$$

$$44736 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 6$$

$$44737 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 7$$

$$44738 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 8$$

$$44739 := ((F(4) \times F(4))! - 7!) / F(3!) + 9$$

$$44740 := (4 \times (((F(F(4)) \times F(F(7))) \times 4!) + 0!))$$

$$44741 := ((F(4!) + 4) - (F(F(7)) \times ((F(4))! + 1)))$$

$$44742 := (((4! \times 4) \times F(F(7))) + F(4)) \times 2$$

$$44743 := ((((-4) - F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + F(4!)) + 3!$$

$$44744 := ((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (4! + F(4)))$$

- 44744** := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (4! + F(4)))$
44745 := $(F(4!) - (4! + (F(7) \times (F(4) + 5!))))$
44746 := $((F(4!) - 4) - F((-7 + 4!)) - F(F(6)))$
44747 := $((F(4!) - (4!)) - F(((7 - F(4)) + F(7))))$
44748 := $((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - F((-7 + 4!)) - (F(8)))$
44749 := $((F((F(4)!)) \times (4! \times F(F(7)))) + (4 + 9))$
44750 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - F(F((5 + 0!))))$
44752 := $((F(F(4)) - (-4!) \times F(F(7))) \times F(((5 - 2)!))$
44753 := $((F(4)! \times ((F(4)!))! + (-7 + 5!)) + (F(3)!))!$
44754 := $((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - ((F(7) \times (5! + (4))))$
44755 := $((-4) + F((F(F(4)) \times 7)) \times 5!) - (5)$
44756 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (5!/F(6)))$
44757 := $((F((F(4)!)) \times (4! \times F(F(7)))) + (F((-5) + F(7))))$
44758 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (5 + 8))$
44759 := $(F(4!) - ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times 75) + F(9)))$
44760 := $(F(4!) - (4! \times (7 + 60)))$
44761 := $(4! + (((-4!) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(6)) + 1))$
44762 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (F(6) + F(2)))$
44763 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (6 + F(3)))$
44764 := $(4 + (((-4!) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(6)) + (4!)))$
44765 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - (6!/5!))$
44766 := $((F(4) \times F(4)) \times (7! - 66))$
44767 := $(4! + (((-4!) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(6)) + 7))$
44768 := $((4 + (4! \times F((7 + 6)))) \times 8)$
44769 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - F(-((6 - 9))))$
44770 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - ((7 \times 0)!))$
44771 := $(F(4!) - F(((4 + 7) + 7) - 1))$
44772 := $((F(4!) - F((F(4) + (7 + 7)))) + F(2))$
44773 := $((F(4!) + F(F(4))) - (F(((7 + 7) + 3))))$
44774 := $((F(4!) + F(4)) - F(((7 + 7) + F(4))))$
44775 := $((F(4) \times F(4)) \times (7! - (F(7) \times 5)))$
44776 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) + (F(7) - F(6)))$
44777 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) + (-7) + F(7))$
44778 := $(F((F(F(4)) + (4!))) - (-7) - (-7) \times F(F(8))))$
44779 := $(F((F(4)!)) + (F(4!) - F(((F(7) + F(7)) - 9))))$

- 44780 := ((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) + (8 + 0!))
 44781 := (F(4!) - (((F(4))!)! × (-F(7))) + ((F(F(8)) + 1)))
 44783 := (-(((4! × 4!) - 7!) - 8!)) - F(F(3))
 44784 := (4! × ((F((4 + 7)) × F(8)) - F(4)))
 44785 := -((F(4!) - (((F(4))!)! × (-7!)) + F((F(8) + (5))))))
 44786 := ((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) + (F(8) - (6)))
 44787 := ((F(4!) - (F(4))!) - ((F(F(7)) - 8) × 7))
 44791 := ((F((F(4))!) × (4! × F(F(7)))) + F((9 + 1)))
 44792 := ((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) + F((9 - F(2))))
 44793 := (((F(4) × F(4)) × 7) × (-9) + 3!!)
 44794 := (F(4!) - ((47 × F(9)) - 4!))
 44795 := ((F(4!) + (4!)) - F((-7) + ((9 - 5)!)))
 44796 := (F(4!) - ((4! - (-7) × F(9))) × 6)
 44797 := (((4^{F(4)}) - 7!) × (-9)) + F(7)
 44798 := (-F(F(4))) + ((F((F(4))!) × (7!/9)) + 8!))
 44799 := ((F((F(4))!) × ((4! × F(F(7))) + 9)) - 9)
 44800 := (((4 + (F(4))!)!)/(80 + 0!))
 44801 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (((F((F(4))!)!)/(8 + 0!)) + 1))
 44802 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (((F((F(4))!)!)/(8 + 0!)) + 2))
 44803 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (F(4) + (8!/(0! + F(3!))))))
 44804 := (((4⁴) + F(F(8))) - 0!) × 4
 44805 := ((F(4!) - F(4)) + (F((8 - 0!) × (-5!)))
 44806 := ((F(4!) - ((F(4))!)! - (F(F(8))/F((0! + (6))))))
 44807 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (((F((F(4))!)!)/(8 + 0!)) + 7))
 44809 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (((F((F(4))!)!)/(8 + 0!)) + 9))
 44824 := ((F(4!) - ((F(4))!)! - 824)
 44826 := (F(4!) - ((4! × (8²)) + (6)))
 44829 := (((F(4))!)! + (((F(4))!)! + F((F(8) - 2))) × 9))

 44830 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3)! + 0
 44831 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3)! + 1
 44832 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3)! + 2
 44833 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3)! + 3
 44834 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3)! + 4
 44835 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3)! + 5

$$44836 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3!)! + 6$$

$$44837 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3!)! + 7$$

$$44838 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3!)! + 8$$

$$44839 := F(4!)/F(4) - F(F(8)) + F(3!)! + 9$$

$$44840 := (F(4!) - (F((F(4))!) \times ((8 \times 4!) - 0!)))$$

$$44843 := ((F(4!) - F((-4) + F(8))) + (4! \times 3))$$

$$44844 := (F(4!) - (((4! \times F(8)) + (4)) \times F(4)))$$

$$44844 := (F(4!) - (((4! \times F(8)) + (4)) \times F(4)))$$

$$44845 := (((-(4!)!)/F((F(4))!))/F(8)! + ((F(4!) - (5))))$$

$$44847 := (F(4!) - ((-F(4)) + ((8 - F(4))!) \times F(7)))$$

$$44848 := (F(4!) - (((F(4) \times F(8)) \times 4!) + 8))$$

$$44849 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (((F((F(4))!))! + (F(8)^{F(F(4))})/9))$$

$$44850 := (F(4!) - (((4!)!)/F(8)!)/F((5 + 0!)))$$

$$44853 := (-F(4)) + ((4! \times F(8)) \times F((5 + 3!)))$$

$$44854 := (-F(F(4))) + ((4! \times F(8)) \times F((5 + (F(4))!)))$$

$$44856 := (F(4!) - ((4 + 8) \times (5! + (6))))$$

$$44857 := (((F(4))!)! + (((4 \times F(F(8))) + 5!) + F(F(7))))$$

$$44859 := -((F(F((F(4))!)) - (((F(4) + 8) \times 5!) \times F(9))))$$

$$44860 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 0$$

$$44861 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 1$$

$$44862 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 2$$

$$44863 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 3$$

$$44864 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 4$$

$$44865 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 5$$

$$44866 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 6$$

$$44867 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 7$$

$$44868 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 8$$

$$44869 := F(4!) - 4 \times F(8 + 6) + 9$$

$$44871 := ((F(4!) - (F(4))!) + (F(8) \times (-71)))$$

$$44872 := (-((4! \times F(4))) + ((-F(8)) + F(F(7)))^2))$$

$$44873 := ((((((F(4) \times F(4))!)/8) + F(F(7))) - 3!))$$

$$44874 := (F(4!) - (4! + ((8! - 7!)/4!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44875 &:= ((4! \times ((F(4))! - (-8) \times F(F(7)))) - (5)) \\ 44876 &:= (-4) + (-4!) \times ((-8) \times F(F(7)) - 6)) \\ 44877 &:= ((4 - ((F(4))!))! - (-((8! + 7!) - F(F(7)))) \\ 44878 &:= (((F(4) \times F((-4) + F(8)))) - F(F(7))) + 8! \\ 44880 &:= (-4!) \times ((F((F(4) + 8)) \times (-F(8))) - 0!) \\ 44883 &:= (((4!^{F(4)}) + 8!) - (F(8)^3)) \\ 44884 &:= (((F(4))! \times ((-F(4)) \times F(F(8))) + 8!)) - F((F(4))!) \\ 44886 &:= (F(4!) - (F((4!/8)) \times (F(8) + 6!))) \\ 44888 &:= (4 \times ((F(4!)/(8 \times F(8))) + F(F(8)))) \\ 44889 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((F(4) + 8)) + (8!/9))) \\ 44892 &:= (F(4!) - ((4! + (F(8) \times F(9))) \times 2)) \\ 44893 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) + (4 \times (F(F(8)) - (-F(9)) \times F(3!)))) \\ 44894 &:= (F(4!) - (F(F(4)) \times (8 + (9^{F(4)})))) \\ 44895 &:= (F(4!) - ((-4) + F((8 + 9))) - 5!) \\ 44896 &:= (((4! \times 4) + (8!/9)) + (F(6))!) \\ 44897 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(F(4)) + (F(8))) \times (-F(9)) + F(F(7)))) \\ 44904 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4))! + F((9 + 0!))) \times 4!)) \\ 44910 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4))! + 9) \times (1 + 0!))) \\ 44912 &:= (F(4!) + (F((F(4))!) \times (-91 \times 2))) \\ 44913 &:= ((F(4!) - ((F(4))!))! - ((F(9) + 1) \times F(F(3!)))) \\ 44916 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(4))! \times (9 + F(F((1 + 6)))))) \\ 44919 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((F(F(4))^9) - 1) \times 9)) \\ 44920 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(4!)/(F(9) - 2)) - 0!)) \\ 44922 &:= (F(4!) - (((4 + F(9))^2) + 2)) \\ 44923 &:= ((F(4!) - (((4 + F(9))^2))) - F(F(3))) \\ 44926 &:= ((F(4!) - (-((F(4) - 9)))! - (2 + 6!)) \\ 44927 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4))! \times 9) + (F(2) - 7!))) \\ 44929 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F(F(F(4))) + (9 \times (2^9)))) \\ 44930 &:= (F(4!) - (F(F(4)) \times (((9 - 3))! - 0!))) \\ 44932 &:= (F(4!) - (-4) + (((9 - 3))! \times 2)) \\ 44933 &:= (((F(4!) - ((4 - 9))) - 3!) - 3!) \\ 44934 &:= ((F((4! + F(4))) - (9!/F(3))) \times F(4)) \\ 44935 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + (4! \times F(9))) \times F((F(3) \times 5))) \\ 44936 &:= (((-4) - (4! \times (-9)))^{F(3)}) - F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$44937 := (((-4) - (4! \times (-9)))^{F(3)} - (7))$$

$$44938 := ((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - (((F(9) \times F(3)) \times F(8))))$$

$$44939 := ((F(4!) - F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(9) + F(3!)) \times F(9)))$$

$$44940 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 0$$

$$44941 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 1$$

$$44942 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 2$$

$$44943 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 3$$

$$44944 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 4$$

$$44945 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 5$$

$$44946 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 6$$

$$44947 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 7$$

$$44948 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 8$$

$$44949 := F(4!) - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(4)) + 9$$

$$44950 := -((F((4! + (4))) - ((9! - 5!) + 0!)))$$

$$44952 := (4! \times (F(4) + (F(9) \times F((5 \times 2))))))$$

$$44955 := ((F(4)^4) \times ((9 - 5!) \times (-5)))$$

$$44956 := (F(4!) - (F(F(4)) \times (-((9 + 5)) + 6!)))$$

$$44957 := ((F(4) + F((F(4)!)) \times ((F(9) \times 5!) + (7))))$$

$$44958 := (F(4!) + (((4! - F(9)) \times (5! + F(8))))))$$

$$44959 := (F(4!) - ((F(4!) - (9^5))/(-9)))$$

$$44961 := ((F(4!) - ((F(4)!))!) + (((F(9) - 6!) - 1)))$$

$$44962 := (F(F(F(4))) \times (F(4!) + (F(9) - (6! \times 2))))$$

$$44963 := (F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) + (F(9) - (6! \times F(3))))))$$

$$44964 := ((F((4! - (4))) + (9 + 6!)) \times (F(4)!))$$

$$44965 := (F(4!) - ((F((4 + 9)) \times 6) + (5)))$$

$$44966 := (F(4!) - (((-4) - F(9)) + 6!) + 6!))$$

$$44967 := ((F(4!) - F(4)) - (((9 - 6)! \times F(F(7))))$$

$$44969 := ((4 + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times 9)) \times F(-((F(F(6)) - F(9))))))$$

$$44970 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 0$$

$$44971 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 1$$

$$44972 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 2$$

$$44973 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 3$$

$$44974 := F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}44975 &:= F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 5 \\44976 &:= F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 6 \\44977 &:= F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 7 \\44978 &:= F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 8 \\44979 &:= F(4!) + (F(4) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 9 \\44980 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((4 + 9)) \times (F(8) - 0!))) \\44981 &:= ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times ((F(4) \times F(9)) \times F(8))) - 1) \\44982 &:= (F(4!) - (((4! + 9) \times F(8)) \times 2)) \\44983 &:= (((F(4) + (4)))! \times 9) - F((8 + 3!)) \\44984 &:= (-(((4! \times (4! + F(9))) - 8)) + F(4!)) \\44987 &:= (((F(4)!)/(-F(F(4)))) - ((9!/(-8)) + F(7))) \\44988 &:= ((F(4)! + (((F(4) \times F(9)) \times F(8)) \times F(8))) \\44989 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times 9) - (8!/(-9)))) \\44990 &:= ((F(F(4) + (4! \times F(9))) \times F((9 + 0!))) \\44992 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times ((F(4)!))! - F(9)) \times (F(9) - 2)) \\44994 &:= (((F((F(4)!))!)/(-4!)) - ((F(9) \times (-9)) - F(4!))) \\44996 &:= (F(4!) - (49 \times (F(9) - (6)))) \\44997 &:= -((F((4! + (4))) - (9! - (9!/7!))) \\44999 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(4)! + F(9)) \times F(9)) + 9)) \\45015 &:= ((F(4) \times F((5^{0!+1}))/5) \\45024 &:= (F(4!) - (F(F((5 + 0!)) \times (2^{F(4)!}))) \\45037 &:= (F(4!) + (((5! + 0!) \times (F(3) - F(7)))) \\45038 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5 + 0!)!) - F(-(3! - F(8)))) \\45039 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((5! + 0!) \times 39)) \\45045 &:= ((F(4) \times F(F((5 + 0!)))) \times (((F(4)!))! - (5))) \\45048 &:= (F(4!) - (5! \times (F(04) + 8))) \\45053 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5! - 0!) \times 5)) - 3!) \\45063 &:= (F(4) \times (-5!) + ((0! + 6!) \times F(F(3)))) \\45064 &:= ((F(4!) - F((5 + 0!))) - (6^4)) \\45069 &:= (((4 + 5)! - F(((0 - 6) + F(9)))) \\45075 &:= (((F(4)!))! - ((5! - 0!)) \times 75) \\45077 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-50) + 7!) - F(F(7))) \\45092 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + (F(09)^2))) \\45093 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - 0!) + (F(9)^{F(3)})))\end{aligned}$$

- 45099 := (F(4!) - ((5! + F(-((0! - 9)))) × 9))
- 45108 := (F(4!) + ((-5) - F(10)) × F(8))
- 45114 := (((F(4))! × (-5! + F(11)))) + F(4!)
- 45117 := (-F(4) - (5! × (1 - F((1 + F(7))))))
- 45127 := (((4 + 5)! / F((1 + 2)!)) - F(F(7)))
- 45135 := ((F(4!) + 5!) + (F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) / (-5)))
- 45136 := (F(4!) - ((F((5 + 1))³) + 6!))
- 45141 := (F(F((F(4))!)) + ((5! × (F(14) - 1))))
- 45142 := (F(4!) - ((51 × 4!) + 2))
- 45143 := ((F(4!) - (51 × 4!)) - F(F(3)))
- 45144 := (4! × ((5 × F(14)) - (4)))
- 45147 := -((F((F(F((F(4))!)) - (5))) + ((1 - F(4!)) + F(F(7)))))
- 45148 := (F(4!) - (F(F((5 - 1))) × F(-(((F(4))! - (F(8)))))))
- 45153 := (F(4!) - (-5) + (F(15) × F(3)))
- 45159 := (F(4!) - (5! + ((-1 - 5!) × (-9))))
- 45163 := (F(4!) - (-5) × (-1 - (6!/3)))
- 45164 := (((-4) × (5! + 1)) - 6!) + F(4!)
- 45167 := ((F(4!) - (((5! + 1) × F(6)))) - F(F(7)))
- 45168 := (F(4!) - ((5 × ((1 + 6)!)/F(8)))
- 45169 := (F(4!) - ((5 × F(F((1 + 6)))) + F(9)))
- 45173 := (F(4!) - (-5) × ((-1) × F(F(7)) - 3!))
- 45174 := (F(4!) - ((-5) × (-1 - F(F(7)))) + (4!))
- 45176 := (F(4!) - ((5 + F((-1 + F(7)))) × F(6)))
- 45179 := (F((F(4))!) + ((F(F((5 + 1))) - (7!)) × (-9)))
- 45198 := (((F(4))!⁵⁻¹) - 9!) / (-8)
- 45203 := (F(4!) - (F(F((5 + 2))) × (-0! - 3!)))
- 45207 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (((5! × (-2)) - 0!) × F(F(7)))))
- 45208 := (F(4!) - (-5) × (F(2) - F(F(-((0! - 8))))))
- 45211 := (F(4!) - ((F((5 + 2)) × F(11)))
- 45212 := (F(4!) - (F(((5 × 2) - 1)²)))
- 45213 := (F(4!) - (-5) × (2 - F(13)))
- 45214 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) × (-F((5 × 2)))) + (1 + F(4!)))
- 45216 := -((4! - (5! × F((2 × (1 + 6))))))
- 45218 := (F(F(4)) × ((F(((5 - 2)!))! - F((1 + F(8))))))
- 45223 := (F(4) - 5! × 2)² - F(F(F(3!)))

$$\begin{aligned} 45224 &:= (F(4!) - (52 \times (-2) + 4!)) \\ 45228 &:= (F(4!) - (5 \times 228)) \\ 45232 &:= -((F((F(4))!) - (5! \times F(((F(2) + 3!) \times 2)))))) \\ 45233 &:= (((4! - (5 + 2))^3) + (F(3))!) \\ 45234 &:= (F((F(4) + (5))) \times ((2 - 3!) \times (-F(4)))) \\ 45235 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((-5!) + ((F(2) + 3!)!) - (5))) \\ 45236 &:= (-4) + (5! \times F(((2^3) + 6))) \\ 45237 &:= -((((F(4) + 5!) - (2^3)!) - 7!)) \\ 45238 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (5! \times F(((2 \times 3) + 8)))))) \\ 45239 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (5! \times F(((2 + 3) + 9)))))) \\ 45240 &:= (F((4 + (5 \times 2))) \times ((4 + 0!)!) \\ 45241 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (5! \times F((2 \times ((F(4))! + 1)))))) \\ 45242 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((5! \times F(((2^4) - 2)))))) \\ 45243 &:= (F(4) + (5! \times F((2 + (4 \times 3)))))) \\ 45244 &:= (4 + (5! \times F(-((2 - (4 \times 4)))))) \\ 45245 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - ((-5) - ((F(2) + (F(4))!)!) + 5!)) \\ 45246 &:= ((F(4))! + (5! \times F(((2 \times 4) + 6)))) \\ 45247 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((-((5! - F(2))) + (F(4))!) + (7!))) \\ 45248 &:= (4 \times (((5! + 2) \times F(4)) + F(F(8)))) \\ 45249 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((-5!) + ((F(2) + (F(4))!)!) + 9)) \\ 45255 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - (-5) \times F((F(F((F(2) + (5)))) - (5)))) \\ 45260 &:= (((F(4!) - 5!) - F((2 \times F(6)))) - 0!) \\ 45261 &:= ((F(4!) - 5!) - F((2 \times F((6 \times 1)))))) \\ 45262 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5! - F(2)))) - F((F(6) \times 2))) \\ 45263 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5! - 2))) - F((F(6) \times F(3)))) \\ 45264 &:= (F(4!) - ((52 - 6) \times 4!)) \\ 45265 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - (-5) \times (2 + F((F(F(6)) - (5)))))) \\ 45268 &:= (F(4!) - ((52 \times F(F(6))) + 8)) \\ 45271 &:= ((F(4!) - (((5 - 2))!)!) - F((F(7) + 1))) \\ 45273 &:= -((((F(((F(4))! + (5))) + (-2) - 7!) - (F(3))!)) \\ 45274 &:= (((F(F(4)) + 5!) \times F((2 \times 7))) - ((F(4))!)) \\ 45276 &:= (F(4!) - ((-5) + F((2 \times 7))) + 6!) \\ 45277 &:= (4! + ((5! \times F((2 \times 7))) + F(7))) \\ 45279 &:= (((-4) + F((5 + 2))) - 7!) \times (-9) \\ 45280 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((5 + 2)! - (80))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45284 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! \times (F(2) + 8)) + (4))) \\45287 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((-52) - F(8)) + 7!) \\45288 &:= (F(4!) - (5! \times ((F(2)^8) + 8))) \\45289 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + (((5 + 2)! - 8) \times 9)) \\45292 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((5 + 2)! + (F(9) \times (-2)))) \\45294 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - F(2)) \times 9) + F(4))) \\45295 &:= (F(4!) + ((5 + 2) - (9 \times 5!))) \\45296 &:= (((4 + 5)! - (2^9)) / F(6)) \\45299 &:= (((F(4) - ((5 + 2)! \times (-9)) - F(9)) \\45304 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!) - F((3! + 0!))) + F(4!)) \\45306 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - F(3)) \times (0! + F(6)))) \\45307 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (-53) + (07!)) \\45308 &:= (F(4!) - (-53) \times (0! - F(8))) \\45309 &:= -(((F(4)! - ((-5) + ((3! + 0!)! \times 9))) \\45312 &:= (((F((F(4)!))^5) - (F(3)!)) \times (-((1 + 2)!)) \\45314 &:= ((F((4 + 5)) \times (-31)) + F(4!)) \\45318 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((5 + F(F((3! + 1)))) \times F(8))) \\45319 &:= (F(4!) + (5 - (31 \times F(9)))) \\45323 &:= ((-((4^5)) - F(F(3!))) + F(((F(2) + 3)!)) \\45324 &:= (((4 - 5!) \times (3^2)) + F(4!)) \\45325 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((-5) + 3!! \times (2 + 5))) \\45326 &:= -((F((4 + 5)) - (((3^2)! / F(6)))) \\45327 &:= (F(4) \times (-5) + (3 \times (-2) + 7!)) \\45328 &:= (F(4!) - (53 + F((2 \times 8)))) \\45330 &:= (((4 + 5)! / F(3!)) - 30) \\45331 &:= ((-((4! + 5))) + (F(3)!)) + ((3! + 1)!) \\45332 &:= (F(4!) + ((5! - (F((3 \times 3))^2))) \\45333 &:= ((F(4) - ((5 + F(3))!)) \times (-3 \times 3)) \\45334 &:= (((4 + 5)! / F(3!)) - (F(3) + 4!)) \\45335 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (-((5^{F(3)})) + ((F(3) + 5)!)) \\45336 &:= -((4! - ((F((5 + 3)) \times 3) \times 6!)) \\45337 &:= ((-((4! - ((5 + 3)!)) + F(F(3))) + 7!)) \\45338 &:= ((-((4^5)) - 3!) + F((3 \times 8))) \\45339 &:= (F(4) \times ((5^{3!}) - (F(3)^9))) \\45340 &:= ((-(((4^5) + 3)) + F(4!)) - 0!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45341 &:= (-((4^5) + 3)) + F(((4 \times 1)!)) \\
 45343 &:= ((-((4^5)) - F(F(3))) + F((4 \times 3!))) \\
 45345 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 - 3!) + (4^5))) \\
 45347 &:= (((4 + 5) \times ((3 + 4)!)) - F(7)) \\
 45348 &:= (F(4!) - ((5!/F(3)) \times (-4 + F(8)))) \\
 45349 &:= (((((4 + 5)!/F(3!)) - F(F(4))) - 9) \\
 45350 &:= ((-((4^5)) + 3!) + F(((5 - 0)!))!) \\
 45351 &:= ((4 + 5) \times (((F(3) + (5)))! - 1)) \\
 45352 &:= (((((4 + 5)!/F(3!)) - F((5 - 2)!)) \\
 45353 &:= (((((4 + 5)!/F(3!)) - (5 + F(3))) \\
 45354 &:= (((((4 + 5)!/(3 + 5)) - (F(4))!) \\
 45354 &:= (((((4 + 5)!/(3 + 5)) - (F(4))!) \\
 45356 &:= (((((4 + 5)! - (F(3)^5))/F(6)) \\
 45357 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((-5) + ((3 + 5)! + 7!)) \\
 45358 &:= (((((4 + 5)!/F(3!)) - F(-((5 - 8)))) \\
 45359 &:= ((4 - 5) + (((F(3) + (5)))! \times 9)) \\
 \\
 45360 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 0 \\
 45361 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 1 \\
 45362 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 2 \\
 45363 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 3 \\
 45364 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 4 \\
 45365 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 5 \\
 45366 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 6 \\
 45367 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 7 \\
 45368 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 8 \\
 45369 &:= F(4) \times F(5 + 3) \times 6! + 9 \\
 \\
 45370 &:= (((4 + 5) \times (F(F(3)) + (7!))) + 0!) \\
 45371 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times 5) + (F(3!))!) + (7! + 1)) \\
 45372 &:= (F(4) \times (5 + ((3 \times 7!) - F(2)))) \\
 45373 &:= ((F(4) \times (5 + (3 \times 7!))) - F(3)) \\
 45374 &:= (((4 + 5) \times (F(3) + 7!)) - (4)) \\
 45375 &:= (F(4) \times (((5 - F(3)) \times 7!) + (5))) \\
 45376 &:= (((4! + ((5 + 3)!)) + 7!) - F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45378 &:= (((F(4) + (5 \times 3)) + 7!) + 8!) \\ 45379 &:= (-((4 - 5)) + ((F(3) + 7!) \times 9)) \\ 45380 &:= (F(4!) - (F(((5 + 3) + 8)) + 0!)) \\ 45381 &:= (F(4!) - F(((5 + 3) + 8) \times 1)) \\ 45382 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 - 3!) + F((8 \times 2)))) \\ 45383 &:= (F(4!) - (F(((5 + 3) + 8)) - F(3))) \\ 45384 &:= (((F(4) \times 5!) \times 3!) \times F(8)) + 4! \\ 45385 &:= (((F(4!) + (5)) - F(F(3))) - F((F(8) - (5)))) \\ 45386 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! + F(3)) \times 8) + (6))) \\ 45387 &:= (((F(4) + 5!)^{F(3)}) \times F(8)) / 7 \\ 45388 &:= (F(4!) - ((-5) - F(3)) + F((8 + 8))) \\ 45389 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 3!) \times 89)) \\ \\ 45390 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 0 \\ 45391 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 1 \\ 45392 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 2 \\ 45393 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 3 \\ 45394 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 4 \\ 45395 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 5 \\ 45396 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 6 \\ 45397 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 7 \\ 45398 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 8 \\ 45399 &:= F(4!) - F(-5 + F(F(3!))) + 9 + 9 \\ \\ 45402 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + ((F(4!) - ((0! + 2)!))) \\ 45403 &:= ((F(4!) - (5)) - (((4 + 0)! \times F(3!))) \\ 45404 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! \times F(F(4))) + 0!) \times 4)) \\ 45405 &:= ((-((F(4)^5)) + F(4!)) - ((0! + (5)!)) \\ 45406 &:= ((-((F(4)^5)) + F(4!)) + (0! - 6!)) \\ 45407 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + ((F(4!) - ((0 \times 7)!))) \\ 45408 &:= (F(4!) - (5! \times ((4 \times 0) + 8))) \\ 45409 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + ((F(4!) + ((0 \times 9)!))) \\ 45410 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + ((F(4!) + (1 + 0!))) \\ 45413 &:= ((F(4!) + (5)) - (((4 + 1)! \times F(3!))) \\ 45414 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! \times F(((4 - 1)!)) - (F(4)!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45415 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) - (((1 + 5)!)) \\ 45416 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 \times 4!) - 1) \times F(6))) \\ 45423 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5 \times F(4))^2)) - 3!!) \\ 45424 &:= (((F(F(4)) - 5!) \times (4 \times 2)) + F(4!)) \\ 45426 &:= ((45 + F(4!)) - F((2 \times F(6)))) \\ 45427 &:= ((F(4!) - (5)) - (4 \times (F(2) + F(F(7)))))) \\ 45428 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + ((F(4!) - ((F(2) - F(8)))))) \\ 45429 &:= (((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + F(4!)) + F(-((F(2) - 9)))) \\ 45430 &:= (((F((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)) + F(4!)) + F(F(3!))) + 0!) \\ 45431 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - F(4)) \times F(3!)) + 1)) \\ 45432 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - F(4)) \times F((3 \times 2)))) \\ 45433 &:= ((F(4!) - (5 \times 43)) - 3!!) \\ 45434 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - (4)) \times F(3!)) + (F(4)!))) \\ 45435 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - (4)) \times F(3!)) + (5))) \\ 45436 &:= -(((F(F(4)) \times F((5 \times F(4)))) - (3!^6))) \\ 45437 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + F((4 + 3))) \times 7)) \\ 45438 &:= (F(4) \times (-5!) + (((F(4)! \times (3!)) + F(F(8)))))) \\ 45439 &:= (((-((F(4)^5)) + F(4!)) - 3!!) + F(9)) \\ \\ 45440 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 \\ 45441 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 \\ 45442 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 \\ 45443 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 \\ 45444 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 \\ 45445 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 \\ 45446 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 \\ 45447 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 \\ 45448 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 \\ 45449 &:= F(4!) + (-5! + 4) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 \\ \\ 45450 &:= (((-(((4 + 5)!)) - ((F(4)!)))/(-F((5 + 0!)))) \\ 45453 &:= ((45 + F(4!)) + (-5!) \times F(3!)) \\ 45456 &:= -(((4! - 5!) - (((4 + 5)!)/F(6))) \\ 45457 &:= (F(4!) + ((5! - ((4^5) + 7))) \\ 45459 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 - 4!) + 5!) \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45463 &:= (F(4!) - (5 + ((4! + (6))^{F(3)}))) \\
 45464 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - (4)) \times F(6)) - 4!)) \\
 45465 &:= (F((F(4) + (5))) \times ((F(4) \times 6!) + (5))) \\
 45466 &:= (((F(4!)/(5 + 4)) - 6) + (F(6)!)) \\
 45467 &:= (F(4!) - ((54 \times F(F(6))) - F(F(7)))) \\
 45468 &:= (F(4) + ((5 + (F(4) \times 6!)) \times F(8))) \\
 45469 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) \times 5) - (F(F((F(4)!))^{-6+9})) \\
 45471 &:= (F(4!) + (((-5!) - F((F(4)!)) \times 7) - 1)) \\
 45472 &:= ((-(((4 + 5)!)) - F(4!))/(-7 + 2)) \\
 45473 &:= (((F(4!) - 5!) - F((F(4) + (7)))) - 3!!) \\
 45474 &:= (((F(4!) + 5!)/(-4 \times F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 45475 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((5 \times 4!) + 7!) - (5))) \\
 45476 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! + (4)) \times F(7)) - 6!)) \\
 45477 &:= (((F(4) \times (-5)) + 4!) \times (7! + F(7))) \\
 45478 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((5! - (4)) + 7!) + 8!)) \\
 45479 &:= (((-4) + 5!) + F(4)) + (7! \times 9)) \\
 45480 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((5 \times 4!) + ((8 - 0)!))!) \\
 45481 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) - ((-5!) - F(F(F(4)))) - ((8 - 1)!)) \\
 45482 &:= (F(F(4)) + (5! \times (F((F(4)! + 8)) + 2))) \\
 45483 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5! + 4!) + F(8))) - 3!!) \\
 45484 &:= ((4 + 5!) + (((F(4)!))! \times (F(8) \times F(4)))) \\
 45485 &:= ((-(4^5) + F(4!)) + ((F(8) + 5!))) \\
 45486 &:= ((F(4)! + (5! + ((F(4) \times F(8)) \times 6!))) \\
 45487 &:= (((4 + 5!) + F(4)) + 8!) + 7! \\
 45488 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F((5! + 4!)/8)) + 8!) \\
 45489 &:= (-((F(4)!)) + (((-5!) - (F((F(4)!))!)/8) \times (-9))) \\
 45491 &:= (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (F((-5) + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (F(9) + 1))) \\
 45492 &:= (((F(4!) - 5!) - ((F(4)!))! - ((F(9) + 2))) \\
 45493 &:= (F(4!) - ((5^{F(4)}) \times (9 - F(3)))) \\
 45494 &:= (F(4!) - (((5^{F(F(4))}) \times F(9)) + (4!))) \\
 45495 &:= ((4! + F((-5) + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (9 \times 5)) \\
 45496 &:= ((4 \times F((5 + 4))) + (9!/F(6))) \\
 45497 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - 4!) \times 9) + (7))) \\
 45498 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 4!) \times (9 + F(8))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45499 &:= (((F(4)^5) + F(4!)) + 9!) / 9 \\45504 &:= (((F(4!) - 5!) - ((5 + 0!)!) - (4!)) \\45507 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + F((5 - 0!))) \times 7)) \\45518 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 \times 5) \times F((1 + 8)))) \\45519 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + ((5 + 1)!) + 9)) \\45523 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + (5)) + ((2 \times 3)!)) \\45524 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! \times (5 + 2)) + (4))) \\45526 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + F((5 - 2))) + 6!)) \\45528 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! / (5 - 2)) \times F(8))) \\45532 &:= (((F(4!) + (5 - 5!)) - 3!) - F(2)) \\45533 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - (5)) + ((3 + 3)!)) \\45534 &:= ((F(4!) - (5! \times (5 + F(3)))) + (F(4)!)) \\45535 &:= ((F(4!) + (5! \times (-5))) - F(F((F(3) + (5)))))) \\45536 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - (5 + 3)) + 6!)) \\45537 &:= (F(4!) - (5 + ((5! - F(3)) \times 7))) \\45539 &:= ((F(4!) + (5 - 5!)) - (F(F(3!)) \times F(9))) \\45543 &:= ((F(4!) - (5! + (-5) \times F(4))) - 3!!) \\45544 &:= ((F(4!) + 5!) - ((5! - F(F(4))) \times F((F(4)!))) \\45546 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + ((5! - F(4)) \times 6))) \\45547 &:= ((F(4!) + (5)) - ((5! - F(F(4))) \times 7)) \\45549 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - (5)) - 4!) \times 9)) \\45553 &:= ((F(4!) - (5! - ((5 \times 5)))) - 3!!) \\45563 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - (5)) \times F(F(6))) / 3)) \\45564 &:= ((F(4!) - 5!) - ((5! - (6)) \times (F(4)!)) \\45568 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! \times (-5)) / (-6)) \times 8)) \\45573 &:= (F(4!) - (5 \times (5! - (F(7) \times (-3)))))) \\45574 &:= -((((F(4)!))! - (F((5! / 5)) - 74))) \\45577 &:= (F((-((F(F(F(4))) - (5))))!) - ((5! - (7)) \times 7)) \\45579 &:= (F(4) - (((5! / (-5)) - 7!) \times 9)) \\45583 &:= ((F(4!) - (5 \times (5 + 8))) - 3!!) \\45584 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (5)) \times (-5! - 8)) + F(4!)) \\45586 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - (58)) + 6!)) \\45593 &:= (F(4!) - (55 + ((9 - 3)!)) \\45594 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 \times (5! + F(9))) + (4))) \\45596 &:= (((-4) + 5!) + 5!) + (9! / F(6))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45597 &:= -((((F(4) - 5!) - 5!) - (9 \times 7!))) \\ 45598 &:= (((F(4)^5) - (5)) + (9!/8)) \\ 45599 &:= (F(4!) - (-5) - ((5! - F(9)) \times (-9))) \\ 45603 &:= (((F(4)^5) + (F(6))!) + ((0! + 3!)!)) \\ 45604 &:= (((-(45) - 6!) + 0!) + F(4!)) \\ 45606 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! + F(6)) - 0!) \times 6)) \\ 45609 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 6!) + F(09))) \\ 45612 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! + (6)) \times ((1 + 2))!)) \\ 45613 &:= ((F(4!) - (5 \times (6 + 1))) - 3!!) \\ 45614 &:= (-((F((4 + 5)) + 6!)) + F(((1 \times 4)!)) \\ 45617 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + 5!) \times F(((6 + 1) + 7))) \\ 45618 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + (((6 + 1))!/8))) \\ 45619 &:= (F(4!) - ((-5) + 6!) + F((1 \times 9))) \\ 45622 &:= (((F(4!) - (5)) - F(F(6))) - ((F((2 + 2))!)) \\ 45623 &:= ((F(4!) - (5^{F(6/2)})) - 3!!) \\ 45624 &:= (((-(4) - 5!) \times 6) + F(24)) \\ 45626 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 + 6) \times 2) + 6!)) \\ 45627 &:= (F(4!) - (-((5 - 62)) \times F(7))) \\ 45628 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! \times 6) - F(2)) + F(8))) \\ 45630 &:= ((F(4!) + (-5) - 6!) - F((3! + 0!))) \\ 45633 &:= (F(4!) - ((5!/F(6)) + ((3 + 3)!)) \\ 45634 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 + 6!) + 3!) + F(4))) \\ 45635 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 6!) + (3 + 5))) \\ 45636 &:= (F(4!) - ((-5) + F(6)) + ((3^6))) \\ 45637 &:= (F(4!) - (((-5) + 6!) + 3) + F(7)) \\ 45638 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 6!) - ((3 - 8))) \\ 45639 &:= (F(4!) - ((-5) + F(6))^{-3+9}) \\ \\ 45640 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 0 \\ 45641 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 1 \\ 45642 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 2 \\ 45643 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 3 \\ 45644 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 4 \\ 45645 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 5 \\ 45646 &:= -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$45647 := -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 7$$

$$45648 := -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 8$$

$$45649 := -F(4) - 5 - 6! + F(4!) + 9$$

$$45650 := ((F(4!) + (5 - 6!)) - F((5 - 0!)))$$

$$45651 := (F(4!) - ((5! \times 6) - F((5 - 1))))$$

$$45652 := (F(4!) - (((5! \times 6) - (5)) + F(2)))$$

$$45653 := (F(4!) - ((5! + 6!) - ((5^3))))$$

$$45654 := (F(4!) - ((-5) + 6!) - (5 - 4))$$

$$45654 := (F(4!) - ((-5) + 6!) - (5 - 4))$$

$$45655 := ((F(F(4)) + (5 - 6!)) + F((5!/5)))$$

$$45656 := (F(4!) - (((5 + 6) - 5)! - F(6)))$$

$$45658 := (F(4!) - ((5 + 6!) - (5!/8)))$$

$$45659 := ((F(4!) + (5 - 6!)) + (F(-((5 - 9))))!)$$

$$45660 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + 6!) - F(6)) + 0!)$$

$$45661 := (F(4!) - ((-5) + 6!) - F((6 \times 1)))$$

$$45662 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + 6!) - F(6)) - F(2))$$

$$45663 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + 6!) - F(6)) - F(3))$$

$$45664 := (F(4!) - ((5 + 6) \times 64))$$

$$45666 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + F(6)) \times (-6)) + 6!)$$

$$45667 := (F(4!) - (((5! \times 6) - (6)) - F(7)))$$

$$45668 := (F(4!) - ((-((5 - 6)) + 6!) - F(8)))$$

$$45669 := (F(4!) - (F((5 + 6)) + F((6 + 9))))$$

$$45670 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + F(6)) \times F(F(7))) - 0!)$$

$$45672 := (F(4!) - (5! + (F(6) \times 72)))$$

$$45673 := ((F(4!) + (-5) \times (F(6) - F(7)))) - 3!)$$

$$45674 := (F(4!) - (((5 + 6!) - (7)) - 4!))$$

$$45675 := (((4! + 5)) \times F(F(6))) \times 75$$

$$45676 := (F(4!) + (((5!/F(6)) + F(7)) - 6!))$$

$$45677 := (F(4!) + (((5! - 6!) + (-7) \times F(7))))$$

$$45682 := ((F(4!) + (5! \times (-6))) + F((8 + F(2))))$$

$$45683 := ((F(4) \times ((5 + 6!) \times F(8))) + F(3!))$$

$$45684 := (F(4) \times (((5 + 6!) \times F(8)) + F(4)))$$

$$45686 := (F(4!) - (-((5 \times 6) + 8)) + 6!)$$

$$45687 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + 6!) - F(8)) - F(7))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45688 &:= (F(4!) - ((-5) - (6!/(-8))) \times 8) \\
 45692 &:= (F(4!) - (-((F((-5) + F(6)))! - F(9)))^2) \\
 45693 &:= (((4! \times 56) \times F(9)) - 3) \\
 45694 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5!/6) \times F(9))) + (F(4))!) \\
 45698 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 + 6!) - F(9)) - F(8))) \\
 45703 &:= (F(4!) + (((5! + F(7)) \times (0! - 3!))) \\
 45704 &:= (((-4!) \times (-5) - F(F(7))) + 0!) \times F((F(4))!) \\
 45705 &:= ((F(4!) + 57) - ((0! + (5))))! \\
 45706 &:= (F(4!) - ((-57) - 0!) + 6!) \\
 45713 &:= ((F(4!) - (-5) \times F(7)) - (((1 \times 3))!))! \\
 45714 &:= -((((F(4))! - 5!) \times (F((F(7) + 1)) + (4!))) \\
 45720 &:= (F(4) \times (5! - (7! \times (-2) - 0!))) \\
 45721 &:= (((((F(4))!)! \times (5! + (7)))/2) + 1) \\
 45722 &:= (F(4!) - (F((5 + F(7)))/(2 + 2))) \\
 45723 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + 7!)/(2^3))) \\
 45724 &:= (4 + (5! \times (F((7 \times 2)) + (4)))) \\
 45725 &:= (((((F(4))!)! \times (5! + (7)))/2) + (5)) \\
 45726 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - F(7)) \times F(2)) \times 6)) \\
 45727 &:= ((F(4!) - 5!) - (F((F(7) \times 2))/F(F(7)))) \\
 45728 &:= (F(4!) - (5 \times (((7 - 2))! + 8))) \\
 45729 &:= ((F(4) \times 5!) - ((7! + F(2)) \times (-9))) \\
 45732 &:= ((F(4!) - (5)) - ((7!/F(3!)) + F(2))) \\
 45733 &:= (F(4!) - (5 + (7!/F((3 + 3)))) \\
 45734 &:= (F(4!) - (F(((5 + 7) + 3)) + 4!)) \\
 45735 &:= (F(4) \times (5! + ((7! \times 3) + (5)))) \\
 45736 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 - 7!) - F(F(3!)))/(-F(6)))) \\
 45737 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + ((73 \times 7))) \\
 45738 &:= ((4 + 5) \times (7! + (F(3) \times F(8)))) \\
 45739 &:= (((F(4!) + 57) - 3!) + F(9)) \\
 45740 &:= (((F(F((F(4))!)) \times 5!) - F(F(7))) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!)) \\
 45742 &:= (F(4!) - ((5^{7-F(4)} + F(2))) \\
 45743 &:= (F(4!) - ((5^{F(7-4)})^{F(3)})) \\
 45744 &:= (4! + ((5! + (7! \times F(4))) \times F(4))) \\
 45745 &:= (F((-((F(F(F(4))) - (5))))!) - (F(7) + F((F(4) \times 5))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45746 &:= (F(4!) - (-5 + ((7! - 4!) / F(6)))) \\ 45747 &:= (((F(4) \times 5) \times F(F(7))) + (4!)) \times F(7)) \\ 45749 &:= (F(4!) - (F((5 \times (7 - 4)) + 9)) \\ 45753 &:= (F(4!) - (5 + F(((7 + 5) + 3)))) \\ 45756 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - F(7)) - (5)) \times 6)) \\ 45757 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + (7! / 5!)) \times F(7))) \\ 45758 &:= (F(4!) - F((((5 \times 7) / 5) + 8))) \\ 45759 &:= (F(4!) - (575 + F(9))) \\ 45760 &:= (F(4!) + (((5! - (7)) - 6!) - 0!)) \\ 45761 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! - (7)) - 6!) \times (-1))) \\ 45762 &:= (F(4!) + (((5! - (7)) - 6!) + F(2))) \\ 45763 &:= (F(4!) + (((5! - (7)) - 6!) + F(3))) \\ 45764 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! \times (F(7) - F(6))) + (4))) \\ 45766 &:= ((F(4!) + (-5 + F(7))) - F((F(F(6)) - 6))) \\ 45767 &:= ((F(4!) - ((5! \times 7) - (6))) + F(F(7))) \\ 45768 &:= (F(4!) - (5! \times ((7 + 6) - 8))) \\ 45772 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 \times F(7)) + F(F(7))) \times 2)) \\ 45773 &:= (F(4!) + ((5! - (F(7) \times F((7 + 3)))))) \\ 45774 &:= ((F(4!) + ((5! + (7! / (-7)))) + (F(4))!) \\ 45776 &:= (F(4!) + (((-(5 - 7))^7) - 6!)) \\ 45782 &:= ((F(4!) - 5!) - (F(F(7)) \times F(F((8/2)))))) \\ 45784 &:= ((F(4!) - 578) - (F(4))!) \\ 45785 &:= (F(4!) - (578 + 5)) \\ 45786 &:= ((-4!) \times (5 - F(F(7)))) + ((8! - (6))) \\ 45787 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 78) \times 7)) \\ 45789 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times 5!) + ((7! + F(8)) \times 9)) \\ 45790 &:= (F(4!) - (579 - 0!)) \\ 45792 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + F(7)) \times (F(9) - 2))) \\ 45793 &:= (F(4!) - (-5 \times ((F(7) \times (-9)) + F(3)))) \\ 45794 &:= (((F(4))! + (5! + 7!)) / (-9)) + F(4!) \\ 45795 &:= (((F(F(4)) + 5!) + F(F(7))) \times (9 + 5!)) \\ 45796 &:= (4 \times ((5! - F(7))^{F(9-6)})) \\ 45797 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (-5 + ((F(7) \times F(9)) + 7!))) \\ 45798 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + ((F(7) \times F(9)) + 8))) \\ 45799 &:= (((45 + 7!) \times 9) + F(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45804 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + F(8)) \times 04)) \\45807 &:= ((F(4!) - 5!) - (F(8) \times F((0! + (7)))))) \\45819 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((F((5!/8)) + 1) \times 9)) \\45822 &:= ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-5 - F(8))) + F(((2 + 2)!)) \\45823 &:= ((F(4!) + (5! + F((8 + 2)))) - 3!!) \\45824 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! + ((8 \times 2))) \times 4)) \\45827 &:= (F(4!) - (-5) + ((F(8) \times 2) \times F(7))) \\45828 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + ((F(8) - F(2)) \times F(8)))) \\45829 &:= (F(4!) - (-5) - (-((8 \times 2)) \times F(9))) \\45833 &:= (((F((F(4)!)) \times 5) - (F(F(8)) / (-F(3)))) + (F(3)!)) \\45834 &:= ((F((4! - (5 + 8))) \times (-3!)) + F(4!)) \\45838 &:= (45 - ((F(F(8)) / (-F(3))) - 8!)) \\45840 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (5! \times ((8 \times 4!) - 0!)) \\45843 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 \times F(8)) \times (F(4) + F(3)))) \\45844 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! + 8) + F(4)) \times 4)) \\45846 &:= (F(4!) - (58 \times (F(4) + (6)))) \\45847 &:= ((F(4!) - F((5!/8))) + (F((4 + 7)))) \\45848 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! + 8) \times 4) + 8)) \\45851 &:= (F(4!) - (5 + (8^{F(5-1)}))) \\45853 &:= (F(4!) - (-5) \times ((F(8) \times (-5)) + F(3))) \\45854 &:= ((F(4!) - F((5!/8))) + ((5! - 4!)) \\45854 &:= ((F(4!) - F((5!/8))) + ((5! - 4!)) \\45855 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((-5!) - F((F(8) - (5)))) \times (-5)) \\45856 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! \times F(8)) / 5) + F(6))) \\45857 &:= (F(4!) - (((5! \times F(8)) / 5) + (7))) \\45859 &:= ((F(4!) - (5)) - (F(8) \times (-((5 - 9)!)) \\45863 &:= ((F(4!) - (5! + 8)) - F((F(6) + 3!)) \\45864 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 + 8) + F(6)) \times 4!)) \\45868 &:= (F(4!) - (((-5) + F(F(8))) / F(F(6))) - (F(8))) \\45869 &:= (F(4!) - (-5) + ((8! / 6!) \times 9)) \\45870 &:= (((F(4!) - 5!) - F((F(8) - (7)))) - 0!) \\45871 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + F(((8 + 7) - 1)))) \\45872 &:= (((F(4!) - 5!) - F((F(8) - (7)))) + F(2)) \\45873 &:= (F(4!) - ((5! - F(8)) \times (7 - F(3)))) \\45874 &:= (F(4!) + (((5! - F((8 + 7))) - (4))))\end{aligned}$$

- 45876 := (F(4!) + (((5 - 87) × 6)))
 45878 := ((F(4!) - F((5!/8))) + ((F(7) - 8)!))
 45879 := -((F(4) + ((-58) - 7!) × 9))
 45881 := ((F(4!) - (((-((5 - 8)))!)!) + (F(F((8 - 1))))))
 45882 := (F(((F(4))! + (5))) - (-8!) + (F(F(8))/(-2)))
 45883 := (F(4!) - (-5) × (-8) - F((8 + 3)))
 45884 := (F(4!) - ((5! + (8/8)) × 4))
 45886 := (F(4!) - ((5 × F(8)) + F((8 + 6))))
 45887 := (F(4!) - (((-5) + F(8)) + F(8)) × F(7))
 45888 := ((-4) × 5!) + F(((8 + 8) + 8))
 45892 := (F(4!) - ((-5) - F(-((F(8) - F(9)))))) × (-2))
 45893 := (F(4!) - (-5) × (-89) - 3!))
 45894 := ((F(4!) - F((5!/8))) + (F(9) × 4))
 45895 := (((F(4!) - 5!) - F(-((F(8) - F(9)))))) - 5!
 45897 := (F(4!) - (F((5 + 8)) - (F(9) × (-7))))
 45902 := (F(4!) - (F(((5 + 9) - 0!) × 2))
 45903 := (F(4!) - (5 × (90 + 3)))
 45904 := ((F((F(4))!) × (-59) + 0!) + F(4!))
 45906 := (((F(4)⁵) × 9) - 0!) × F(F(6))
 45909 := (F(4!) - ((5 × 90) + 9))
 45912 := (F(4!) - ((5 × 91) + F(2)))
 45913 := ((F(4!) - ((5 × 91))) × F(F(3)))
 45914 := (F(F(F(4))) + (-((5 × 91)) + F(4!)))
 45918 := (F(4!) - ((5 × ((9 + 1))!)/8!))
 45922 := (F(4!) - ((5 × F((9 + 2))) + F(2)))
 45923 := (F(4!) - (5 × (92 - 3)))
 45924 := ((-4) × (5! - 9)) + F(24))
 45926 := ((F((F(F(4)) + (5))) × (-F(9))) + F((-((2 - 6))!))
 45928 := (F(4!) - (5 × ((9 + 2) × 8)))
 45929 := (F(4!) - ((5 × (9²)) + F(9)))
 45931 := ((F(4!) + (5)) - (F(9) × F((3! + 1))))
 45932 := ((F(4!) + (5)) - (F(F((9 - 3)))²))
 45933 := (F(4!) - (-5) × (-93) + 3!))
 45934 := (((F(4))!^{F(-5+9)}) - ((3!)! + F(F(4))))
 45938 := (F(4!) - ((5! - F(9)) × (-3 - 8)))

$$\begin{aligned} 45939 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + F(9)) \times (F(3) + 9))) \\ 45942 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + (F(9) \times (F(4)^2)))) \\ 45943 &:= (F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) + (4! \times F(3)))) \\ 45944 &:= (F(4!) + ((5! - (F(9) \times (4 \times 4)))) \\ 45945 &:= (((F(4))!)! + ((-((5! - 9!))/F((F(4))!)) - 5!)) \\ 45946 &:= ((F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) + 4!)) - F(F(6))) \\ 45948 &:= (F(4!) - (((5 - 9) + 4!) \times F(8))) \\ 45949 &:= (((F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)))) - F((F(4))!)) - F(9)) \\ 45952 &:= (F(4!) - (F((F(-(5 - 9))))!) \times 52)) \\ 45953 &:= (F(4!) - (-5) \times ((F(9) - 5!) + 3)) \\ 45954 &:= (((F(4))! + (F((5 + 9)))) \times 5! - (F(4))!) \\ 45954 &:= (((F(4))! + (F((5 + 9)))) \times 5! - (F(4))!) \\ 45955 &:= (((F(4))! + (F((5 + 9)))) \times 5! - (5)) \\ 45956 &:= (-4) + ((5! \times F((9 + 5))) + 6!) \\ 45960 &:= (((F(4))! + (F((5 + 9)))) \times ((6 - 0))!) \\ 45961 &:= (((F(4))!)! - ((5! - ((9!/F(6)) + 1)))) \\ 45962 &:= (((F(4))!)! - ((5! - ((9!/F(6)) + 2)))) \\ 45963 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 \times 9) \times (6 + 3))) \\ 45964 &:= (F(4!) - ((5 + 96) \times 4)) \\ 45965 &:= (F((F(4) \times 5)) + ((9!/F(6)) - (5))) \\ 45966 &:= (F(4!) - ((59 + F(6)) \times 6)) \\ 45967 &:= ((F(4!) + (((5! - F(9)) - 6!))) + F(F(7))) \\ 45968 &:= (F(4!) - (5! + ((F(9) \times F(6)) + 8))) \\ 45969 &:= (((F(4))!)! - ((5! - ((9!/F(6)) + 9)))) \\ \\ 45970 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 0 \\ 45971 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 1 \\ 45972 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 2 \\ 45973 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 3 \\ 45974 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 4 \\ 45975 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 5 \\ 45976 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 6 \\ 45977 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 7 \\ 45978 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 8 \\ 45979 &:= F(F(4) \times 5) + 9 \times 7! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

- 45981** := $((F(4!) - (5! + F(9))) - F(F((8 - 1))))$
45982 := $(F(4!) - ((F((5 + 9)) + 8) + F(2)))$
45983 := $((F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)))) - F((8 - F(3))))$
45984 := $(F(4!) - (((5 \times 9) \times 8) + 4!))$
45985 := $(F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) + ((8 - 5)!))$
45986 := $((F(4!) + 59) + (-F(8) \times F(F(6))))$
45987 := $((F(4!) + ((5 - 9))) - F((F(8) - (7))))$
45988 := $(F(4!) - (5 \times ((F(9) + F(8)) + F(8))))$
45990 := $(F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) + ((9 \times 0)!))$
45991 := $(F(4!) - F(-(((5 - 9) - 9) - 1)))$
45992 := $(F(4!) - (((5! + F(9)) + F(9)) \times 2))$
45993 := $(F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) - F((9/3))))$
45994 := $(F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) - (9/F(4))))$
45995 := $(F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)) - (9 - 5)))$
45996 := $(F(4!) - (5! + (9 \times (F(9) - (6)))))$
45997 := $((F(4!) - (5! + ((9 + 9)))) - F(F(7)))$
45998 := $-(((F(4) + (-5) \times F(9)) \times F(9)) - 8!))$
46004 := $(F(4!) - ((6!/(0! + 0!)) + (4)))$
46008 := $(F(4!) - (6!/(0! + ((0 \times 8)!)))$
46014 := $((F(4!) - ((6!/(0! + 1)))) + (F(4)!))$
46015 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 01)))) - 5!)$
46024 := $(F((F(4))!) + ((6! - 0!) \times (2^{F(4)!})))$
46025 := $(F(4!) - ((F(6) - 0!)^{-2+5}))$
46026 := $((F(4!) - (6!))/F((0! + 2)!)) + (F(6)!)$
46028 := $(F(4!) - (F((F(6) + 0!)) \times (2 + 8)))$
46031 := $(F(4!) - (((F(6))!)/(-((0! - 3)!))!) + 1))$
46032 := $(F(4!) - ((F(6))!)/((03 + 2)!))$
46033 := $(F(4!) + ((F(6) - ((0! + 3!)^3)))$
46034 := $(((((F((F(4))!) \times F(F(6))) - 0!) \times (-F(3))) + F(4!))$
46038 := $(F(4!) - (6 \times F((F(03) + 8))))$
46040 := $(F(4!) - (F(6) \times (0! + 40)))$
46042 := $((F(4!) + F((F(6) + 0!))) + (((F(4))!)/(-2)))$
46043 := $(F(4!) - (F((F(6) - 0!)) \times (4! + F(F(3))))$
46044 := $(F(4!) - ((6^04)/4))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46045 &:= (((F(4))!^6) - 0!) - F((F(4) \times 5)) \\
 46046 &:= (F(4!)) - ((F(6) - 0!) \times 46) \\
 46047 &:= (F(4!)) - ((F(6) + 0!) + (4! \times F(7))) \\
 46048 &:= (F(4!)) - (F(6) \times ((0! + (4)) \times 8)) \\
 46053 &:= (F(4!)) - (F(F(6)) \times (05 \times 3)) \\
 46055 &:= (((F(4))!^6) - (0! - (5! \times (-5)))) \\
 46056 &:= (F(4!)) + ((F(6) \times (0! - (5 \times F(6)))))) \\
 46059 &:= (F(4!)) - ((60 \times 5) + 9) \\
 46062 &:= (F(4!)) - ((F(6) + 0!) \times F((F(6) + F(2)))) \\
 46063 &:= (F(4!)) - (F(((F(6) - 0!) + F(6)))/F(3)) \\
 46064 &:= (((-4) \times 6!) + 0!) \times (F(6) - 4!) \\
 46064 &:= (((-4) \times 6!) + 0!) \times (F(6) - 4!) \\
 46066 &:= -(((F(4))! + (F(6) \times (0! - (F(6) \times 6)))))) \\
 46067 &:= (((4 + 60) \times 6!) - F(7)) \\
 46068 &:= (-4) + (((6! - 0!) \times F(6)) + 8!) \\
 46071 &:= (((F(4))!)! + (((F(6) + 0!) \times (7! - 1)))) \\
 46073 &:= (((F(4!)) - 60) - F(F(7))) - F(3) \\
 46074 &:= (F(4!)) - (6 - ((0! - F(7)) \times 4!)) \\
 46075 &:= (((4! \times (F(6))!)/F((0! + (7)))) - (5)) \\
 46076 &:= (-4) + ((6! + (07!)) \times F(6)) \\
 46077 &:= ((-((F(4) - 6!)) + ((0! + (7)))!) + (7!)) \\
 46078 &:= -((((F(4) - 6!) - 0!) - 7!) - 8!) \\
 46079 &:= (((F(4!)) - F(F(6))) - 0!) - F(F(7)) - F(9) \\
 \\
 46080 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 0 \\
 46081 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 1 \\
 46082 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 2 \\
 46083 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 3 \\
 46084 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 4 \\
 46085 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 5 \\
 46086 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 6 \\
 46087 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 7 \\
 46088 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 8 \\
 46089 &:= 4! \times F(6)!/F(08) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

- 46093** := $(F(4!) - ((F(6) \times F(09)) + 3))$
46094 := $((F(4!) + (F(6) \times (0 - F(9)))) - F(F(4)))$
46095 := $(F(4!) - ((F(6) - 0!) \times (F(9) + (5))))$
46097 := $(F(4!) + (((F(6) \times (0! - F(9))) - (7))))$
46098 := $(F(4!) - (6 - ((0! - F(9)) \times 8)))$
46104 := $(F(4!) - ((F(F(6)) - 10) \times 4!))$
46106 := $(F(4!) - (6 + ((1 + 0!)^{F(6)})))$
46108 := $(F(4!) + ((F((6 + 1)) \times (0! - F(8))))$
46112 := $(F(4!) - (((F(6) \times (1 + 1))^2)))$
46113 := $((F(4!) - F(F(6))) - (1 + F(13)))$
46114 := $((F(4!) - F(F(6))) - F(F((11 - 4))))$
46115 := $((F(4!)/F(6)) - 1) + (F((1 + 5)))!$
46116 := $((F(4!)/F(6)) + (((1 + 1) + 6)))!$
46117 := $((F(4!)/F(6)) - (-1 - ((1 + 7)))!)$
46118 := $(F(4!) + ((6 - ((1 + 1)^8)))$
46122 := $(F(4!) - ((F(F(6)) - (F(12))) \times (-2)))$
46123 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) - (2 \times 3!))$
46126 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) - (F(2) + F(6)))$
46127 := $((F(4!) - F(6)) - F(F(((1^2) \times 7)))$
46128 := $(F(4!) - (6!/F((12 - 8))))$
46129 := $((F(4!) - 6) - F(F(-(((1 \times 2) - 9))))$
46130 := $(F(4!) - ((6 + F(13)) - 0!))$
46131 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) - (3 + 1))$
46132 := $(F(4!) - (((6 - 1)! - F(3)) \times 2))$
46134 := $(F(4!) - ((6 \times 13) \times F(4)))$
46135 := $(F(4!) - F((((6 - 1) + 3) + 5)))$
46136 := $(F(4!) - ((6!/(1 \times 3)) - F(6)))$
46140 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (4 + 0!))$
46141 := $(F(4!) - (-6 + F((14 - 1))))$
46142 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (F(4))! + F(2))$
46143 := $(F(4!) - (((6 - 1) \times F(4))^{F(3)}))$
46145 := $(F(4!) - ((6! - F(14)) - 5!))$
46146 := $(F(4!) - ((F((6 + 1)) + 4!) \times 6))$
46147 := $(F(4!) - ((F((6 + 1)) + (4)) \times F(7)))$

- 46148** := $(F(4!) - ((F(F(6)) - 1) \times (F(4) + 8)))$
46149 := $(F(4!) - (((6 + 1)!/4!) + 9))$
46151 := $(F(4!) - ((6^{F(-1+5)} + 1))$
46152 := $(F(4!) - (6^{1^5+2}))$
46153 := $(F(4!) - ((6^{F(-1+5)} - F(F(3))))$
46154 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (-5 + 4!))$
46156 := $((F(4!) + F(F(6))) - F(F((1^5) + 6)))$
46157 := $((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (1^5)) - F(F(7))$
46158 := $(F(4!) - (((6 - 1) + 5) \times F(8)))$
46159 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (-((5 - 9)))!)$
46162 := $(F(4!) - ((6 \times F((1 + F(6)))) + 2))$
46163 := $((F(4!) - 61) - F((6 \times F(3))))$
46164 := $(F(4!) - (-6 + (((1 + 6)!/4!)))$
46164 := $(F(4!) - (-6 + (((1 + 6)!/4!)))$
46165 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (6 \times 5))$
46166 := $((F(4!) - F((F(6) + 1))) - (F(6) \times F(F(6))))$
46168 := $(4! - (((6! + 1) \times F(6)) \times (-8)))$
46169 := $(F(4!) - (F(((6 + 1) + 6)) - F(9)))$
46170 := $((F(4!) + F((F(6) + 1))) - F(F(7))) + 0!$
46173 := $(F(4!) - (((6 - 1) \times F(7)) \times 3))$
46174 := $(F(4!) - (((6 - 1)! + 74))$
46176 := $((4! \times F((F(6) + 1))) + (7!)) + (F(6)!)$
46177 := $((F(4!) - F(F(6))) - (1 + (F(7) \times F(7))))$
46178 := $(F(4!) - ((F((6 + 1)) \times F(7)) + F(8)))$
46180 := $(F(4!) - (F(6) + 180))$
46181 := $(F(4!) - (6 + 181))$
46182 := $(((((4!)!/(F(F(6)))!) - (-1 - F(F(8)))) \times 2)$
46183 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + (8 \times 3!))$
46185 := $(F(4!) - (61 \times (8 - 5)))$
46186 := $(F(4!) - (F((6 + 1)) \times (8 + 6)))$
46187 := $(F(4!) + ((6 - 187)))$
46188 := $(F(4!) - (-6 \times ((-1 - F(8)) - 8)))$
46190 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + F((9 + 0!)))$
46192 := $(F(4!) - ((F(F(6)) + 1) \times (9 - F(2))))$

$$46193 := (F(4!) - ((6 - 1) \times (F(9) + F(F(3))))))$$

$$46194 := (F(4!) - (((6 - 1) \times F(9)) + (4)))$$

$$46195 := (F(4!) - (F(6) + ((-1 + F(9)) \times 5)))$$

$$46196 := (F(4!) - (((F(F(6)) - 1) \times 9) - F(6)))$$

$$46198 := (F(4!) - ((6 - 1) \times F((9!/8!))))$$

$$46200 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 0$$

$$46201 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 1$$

$$46202 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 2$$

$$46203 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 3$$

$$46204 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 4$$

$$46205 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 5$$

$$46206 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 6$$

$$46207 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 7$$

$$46208 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 8$$

$$46209 := F(4!) - F(F(6)) \times F((2 + 0)!) + 9$$

$$46211 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) - (2 \times F(11)))$$

$$46212 := (F(4!) - ((6 \times 2) + F(12)))$$

$$46214 := ((F(4!) - F((F(6) + F(2)))) - (((1 + 4)!)))$$

$$46215 := ((F(4!) - F((F(6) + F(2)))) + (1 - 5!))$$

$$46216 := (F(4!) - (F(6) + F((2 \times 1) \times 6)))$$

$$46217 := (F(4!) - (F((6 \times 2)) + (1 \times 7)))$$

$$46218 := ((F(4!) - 6) - F((-F(2)) + F(-((1 - 8))))))$$

$$46221 := (F(4!) - ((F(6) - F(2)) \times 21))$$

$$46222 := (F(4!) - (((6 \times 2)^2) + 2))$$

$$46223 := (F(4!) - (F((6 \times 2)) - ((2 - 3))))$$

$$46225 := (F(4!) - ((F((6 + 2)) + 2) + 5!))$$

$$46227 := (F(4!) - (((F(6)^2) \times 2) + F(7)))$$

$$46228 := (F(4!) - ((6 \times 22) + 8))$$

$$46230 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 0$$

$$46231 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 1$$

$$46232 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 2$$

$$46233 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 3$$

$$46234 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 4$$

$$46235 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 5$$

$$46236 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 6$$

$$46237 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 7$$

$$46238 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 8$$

$$46239 := F(4!) - 6 \times 23 + 9$$

$$46240 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 0$$

$$46241 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 1$$

$$46242 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 2$$

$$46243 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 3$$

$$46244 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 4$$

$$46245 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 5$$

$$46246 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 6$$

$$46247 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 7$$

$$46248 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 8$$

$$46249 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 2^4 + 9$$

$$46250 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 0$$

$$46251 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 1$$

$$46252 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 2$$

$$46253 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 3$$

$$46254 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 4$$

$$46255 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 5$$

$$46256 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 6$$

$$46257 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 7$$

$$46258 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 8$$

$$46259 := F(4 \times 6) + 2 - 5! + 9$$

$$46260 := (F(4!) - ((6 \times 2) \times (F(6) + 0!)))$$

$$46261 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) - (2^{6+1}))$$

$$46262 := (F(4!) - (6 + ((2 + F(6))^2)))$$

$$46263 := (F(4!) - (F((6 + 2)) \times (F(6) - 3)))$$

$$46265 := (F(4!) + (((F(6) + F(2)) + F(6)) - 5!))$$

$$46266 := (((F(4) + 6!) \times (2^6)) - (6))$$

$$46267 := (F(4!) - (-((6/2)) + (F(6) \times F(7))))$$

$$46268 := (F(4!) - ((F(6) + 2)^{-6+8}))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46269 &:= (F(4!) - (((6/2) + F(6)) \times 9)) \\ 46270 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(6) - F(2)) \times (F(7) + 0!))) \\ 46271 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(6) \times (F(2) - F(7))) - 1))) \\ 46272 &:= ((F(4) + 6!) \times ((2^7)/2)) \\ 46273 &:= (F(4!) - (6 + F(((2 \times 7) - 3)))) \\ 46274 &:= (F(4!) - ((6 - F(2)) + F((7 + 4)))) \\ 46275 &:= ((F(4 \times 6) + (27)) - 5!) \\ 46276 &:= (F(4!) - (F(6) + (((2 \times 7) \times 6))) \\ 46278 &:= (F(4!) - ((6 \times 2) + 78)) \\ 46279 &:= (F(4!) - F((6 + ((2 \times 7) - 9)))) \\ 46280 &:= (F(4!) - ((6 + 2) + 80)) \\ 46281 &:= (F(4!) - (F(6) - (2 - 81))) \\ 46282 &:= (F(4!) - ((6 - 2) + 82)) \\ 46286 &:= (F(4!) + (((6 - 2) - 86))) \\ 46287 &:= (F(4!) - ((-6) \times F(2)) + (87)) \\ 46289 &:= (F(4!) - ((62 + 8) + 9)) \\ \\ 46290 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 0 \\ 46291 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 1 \\ 46292 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 2 \\ 46293 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 3 \\ 46294 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 4 \\ 46295 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 5 \\ 46296 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 6 \\ 46297 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 7 \\ 46298 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 8 \\ 46299 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(-2 + 9) + 9 \\ \\ 46300 &:= (F(4!) - (F((6 + 3)) \times (0! + 0!))) \\ 46302 &:= (F(4!) - (6 + (30 \times 2))) \\ 46303 &:= (F(4!) - (63 + F(03))) \\ 46304 &:= (F(4 \times 6) - ((3 + 0!)^{F(4)})) \\ 46305 &:= (F(4!) - (63 + (0 \times 5))) \\ 46306 &:= (F(4!) - (63 - ((0 \times 6)!)) \\ 46307 &:= (F(4!) - (6 + F((3 + 07)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$46308 := (F(4 \times 6) - (-3) \times (0! - F(8)))$$

$$46309 := (F(4!) - (((F(6) \times 3) + 0!) + F(9)))$$

$$46311 := (F(4!) - ((F(6) \times (3! + 1)) + 1))$$

$$46312 := (F(4!) + ((6 - (31 \times 2))))$$

$$46313 := (F(4!) - F(((6 + 3) + (1^3))))$$

$$46314 := (F(4!) - (((6^3) \times 1)/4))$$

$$46315 := (F(4!) - (F(6) + (3 \times 15)))$$

$$46316 := (F(4!) - ((F(6)/F(3)) \times F((1 + 6))))$$

$$46318 := (F(4!) - ((F(6) \times F(3)) + F((1 + 8))))$$

$$46319 := ((F(4 \times 6) + 3!) - F((1 + 9)))$$

$$46320 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 0$$

$$46321 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 1$$

$$46322 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 2$$

$$46323 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 3$$

$$46324 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 4$$

$$46325 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 5$$

$$46326 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 6$$

$$46327 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 7$$

$$46328 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 8$$

$$46329 := F(4!) - F(6) \times 3 \times 2 + 9$$

$$46330 := (F(4!) - ((6 + F(3)) + (30)))$$

$$46331 := ((F(4 \times 6) - 3!) - (31))$$

$$46334 := (F(4!) - F((((6/3) + 3) + 4)))$$

$$46337 := ((F(4 \times 6) + 3!) - 37)$$

$$46338 := ((F(4 \times 6) - 3!) - ((3 \times 8)))$$

$$46340 := (((F(4 \times 6) - 3) - 4!) - 0!)$$

$$46342 := (((F(4 \times 6) - 3) - 4!) + F(2))$$

$$46343 := (((F(4 \times 6) - 3) - 4!) + F(3))$$

$$46349 := ((F(4 \times 6) - 3!) - (4 + 9))$$

$$46350 := (F(4 \times 6) - (3 \times (5 + 0!)))$$

$$46351 := (F(4!) - (F(6) + (3 + 5 + 1)))$$

$$46353 := ((F(4 \times 6) + 3!) - F((5 + 3)))$$

$$46354 := ((F(4 \times 6) + 3!) - ((5 \times 4)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46359 &:= (F(4 \times 6) - ((3! - (5)) \times 9)) \\ 46364 &:= ((F(4 \times 6) - 3!) + (6 - 4)) \\ 46364 &:= ((F(4 \times 6) - 3!) + (6 - 4)) \\ 46375 &:= ((F(4 \times 6) + 3!) + F((7 - 5))) \\ 46379 &:= (F(4!) + (((6 + 3) - 7) + 9)) \\ 46381 &:= ((F(4 \times 6) + 3!) + (8 - 1)) \\ \\ 46390 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 0 \\ 46391 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 1 \\ 46392 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 2 \\ 46393 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 3 \\ 46394 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 4 \\ 46395 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 5 \\ 46396 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 6 \\ 46397 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 7 \\ 46398 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 8 \\ 46399 &:= F(4!) - 6 \times F(3) + F(9) + 9 \\ \\ 46400 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 00 \\ 46401 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 01 \\ 46402 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 02 \\ 46403 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 03 \\ 46404 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 04 \\ 46405 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 05 \\ 46406 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 06 \\ 46407 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 07 \\ 46408 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 08 \\ 46409 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 09 \\ 46410 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 10 \\ 46411 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 11 \\ 46412 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 12 \\ 46413 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 13 \\ 46414 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 14 \\ 46415 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 15 \\ 46416 &:= 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 16 \end{aligned}$$

- 46417** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 17$
- 46418** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 18$
- 46419** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 19$
- 46420** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 20$
- 46421** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 21$
- 46422** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 22$
- 46423** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 23$
- 46424** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 24$
- 46425** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 25$
- 46426** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 26$
- 46427** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 27$
- 46428** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 28$
- 46429** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 29$
- 46430** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 30$
- 46431** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 31$
- 46432** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 32$
- 46433** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 33$
- 46434** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 34$
- 46435** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 35$
- 46436** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 36$
- 46437** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 37$
- 46438** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 38$
- 46439** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 39$
- 46440** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 40$
- 46441** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 41$
- 46442** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 42$
- 46443** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 43$
- 46444** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 44$
- 46445** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 45$
- 46446** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 46$
- 46447** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 47$
- 46448** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 48$
- 46449** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 49$
- 46450** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 50$
- 46451** := $4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 51$

- $46452 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 52$
- $46453 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 53$
- $46454 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 54$
- $46455 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 55$
- $46456 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 56$
- $46457 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 57$
- $46458 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 58$
- $46459 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 59$
- $46460 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 60$
- $46461 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 61$
- $46462 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 62$
- $46463 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 63$
- $46464 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 64$
- $46465 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 65$
- $46466 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 66$
- $46467 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 67$
- $46468 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 68$
- $46469 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 69$
- $46470 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 70$
- $46471 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 71$
- $46472 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 72$
- $46473 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 73$
- $46474 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 74$
- $46475 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 75$
- $46476 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 76$
- $46477 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 77$
- $46478 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 78$
- $46479 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 79$
- $46480 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 80$
- $46481 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 81$
- $46482 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 82$
- $46483 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 83$
- $46484 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 84$
- $46485 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 85$
- $46486 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 86$

$$46487 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 87$$

$$46488 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 88$$

$$46489 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 89$$

$$46490 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 90$$

$$46491 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 91$$

$$46492 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 92$$

$$46493 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 93$$

$$46494 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 94$$

$$46495 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 95$$

$$46496 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 96$$

$$46497 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 97$$

$$46498 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 98$$

$$46499 := 4! + F(6) + F(4!) + 99$$

$$46500 := (F(4!) + (6 \times (F(F((5 + 0!))) + 0!)))$$

$$46502 := ((F(4!) + (F(6) + 5!)) + ((0! + 2)!))$$

$$46503 := (F(4!) + (((F(6) + 5!) + 0!) + 3!))$$

$$46504 := (F(4!) - (((F(6) - 5!) - (04!)))$$

$$46505 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + ((5! + 0!) - (5)))$$

$$46507 := (F(4!) + ((6 + 5!) + F(07)))$$

$$46508 := (((F(4 \times 6) + 5!) - 0!) + F(8))$$

$$46509 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + ((5 + (0 \times 9)))!)$$

$$46510 := (F(4!) + (((6!/5) - 1) - 0!))$$

$$46511 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) + (5)) \times 11))$$

$$46513 := (F(4!) + ((6!/5) + (1^3)))$$

$$46514 := (F(4!) + (((6!/5) - 1) + F(4)))$$

$$46515 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (5! + (1 + 5)))$$

$$46516 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (5! + (1 + 6)))$$

$$46517 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) + 5!) + F((1 + 7))))$$

$$46518 := (F(4!) + (6 + F(((5 - 1) + 8))))$$

$$46519 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (5! + (1 + 9)))$$

$$46520 := ((F(4!) + F(6)) + F((F((5 + 2)) - 0!)))$$

$$46522 := ((F((F(4) + (6))) + 5!) + F(((2 + 2)!))$$

$$46523 := ((F(4!) + (6 + 5)) + F((2 \times 3!)))$$

$$46525 := (F(4!) + ((6!/5) + F((2 + 5))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46526 &:= (F(4!) + (F(6) + ((5^2) \times 6))) \\ 46527 &:= (((4 - 6!) \times (-5)) - F(2)) \times F(7) \\ 46528 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times 5!) / (-2 - 8))) \\ 46529 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(6) + 5!) - F(2)) + F(9))) \\ \\ 46530 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 0 \\ 46531 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 1 \\ 46532 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 2 \\ 46533 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 3 \\ 46534 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 4 \\ 46535 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 5 \\ 46536 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 6 \\ 46537 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 7 \\ 46538 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 8 \\ 46539 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! - 3! + 9 \\ \\ 46540 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 0 \\ 46541 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 1 \\ 46542 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 2 \\ 46543 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 3 \\ 46544 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 4 \\ 46545 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 5 \\ 46546 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 6 \\ 46547 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 7 \\ 46548 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 8 \\ 46549 &:= F(4)!^6 - 5! + 4 + 9 \\ \\ 46551 &:= (((F(4) \times F(F(6))) + 5!) + F(((5 - 1)!)) \\ 46552 &:= (F(4!) + (F(6) \times ((5 \times 5) - 2))) \\ 46553 &:= ((F(4!) + (65 + 5!)) \times F(F(3))) \\ 46554 &:= (F(4!) + (-6) \times (-55 + 4!)) \\ 46555 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(6) \times 5!) / 5) - (5))) \\ 46556 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + (5! + F((5 + 6)))) \\ 46557 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + ((5! / 5) \times 7)) \\ 46558 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times (-6 - (5^5))) + 8!) \\ 46559 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times (5 \times 5)) - 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$46560 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 0$$

$$46561 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 1$$

$$46562 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 2$$

$$46563 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 3$$

$$46564 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 4$$

$$46565 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 5$$

$$46566 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 6$$

$$46567 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 7$$

$$46568 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 8$$

$$46569 := (4 + 6!) \times 5! - F(6)! + 9$$

$$46570 := (((F(4!) - (6 \times 5)) + F(F(7))) - 0!)$$

$$46571 := ((F(4!) - (6 \times 5)) + F(F((7 \times 1))))$$

$$46572 := (F(4!) + ((6!/5!) \times F((7 + 2))))$$

$$46573 := ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + ((5! - (7)) \times F(3)))$$

$$46574 := (F(4!) + (((6 \times 5) \times 7) - 4))$$

$$46575 := (((F(4)!)!) + ((F(F(6)) - 5!)) \times 75)$$

$$46576 := (F(4!) + (((F(6) + (5)) + F(7)) \times F(6)))$$

$$46577 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times 5) + (F(7) \times F(7))))$$

$$46578 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) - ((5 - 7))) \times F(8)))$$

$$46579 := (F(4!) + (6 + (-5) \times (-7 - F(9))))$$

$$46580 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 0$$

$$46581 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 1$$

$$46582 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 2$$

$$46583 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 3$$

$$46584 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 4$$

$$46585 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 5$$

$$46586 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 6$$

$$46587 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 7$$

$$46588 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 8$$

$$46589 := F(4!) + F(F(6) + 5) - F(8) + 9$$

$$46590 := ((F((F(4)!)!) + ((-(6) + 5!) \times F((9 + 0!))))$$

$$46591 := (((F(4)!)^6) - (5! - F((9 + 1))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46592 &:= (F(4!) + (F(6) \times ((5 + 9) \times 2))) \\ 46593 &:= (F(4!) + (((6!/5!) + 9)^{F(3)})) \\ 46594 &:= (((F(4))!^6) - (59 + F(4))) \\ 46595 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times (-5) + F(9))) - (5))) \\ 46596 &:= (((4! + (6^5)) - F(9)) \times 6) \\ 46597 &:= (F(4!) + (-6) + (5 \times (F(9) + F(7)))) \\ 46598 &:= (F(4!) + (6! - ((5 \times 98)))) \\ 46599 &:= (F(4!) + (F(F(6)) \times ((5 \times 9) - F(9)))) \\ 46600 &:= ((F(4!) + F(((6 + 6) + 0!))) - 0!) \\ 46601 &:= (F(4!) + F(((6 + 6) + 01))) \\ 46602 &:= (F(4!) + (-6) + (6!/(0! + 2))) \\ 46603 &:= ((F(4!) + F(((6 + 6) + 0!))) + F(3)) \\ 46604 &:= ((F(4) + F(((6 + 6) + 0!))) + F(4!)) \\ 46605 &:= ((F(4) - 6!) \times (-60 + 5)) \\ 46606 &:= ((F(4!) + F((F(F(6)) - F(6)))) - ((0! - (6)))) \\ 46607 &:= (F(4!) + (6 + F((6 + 07)))) \\ 46608 &:= (F(4!) + (6! - ((60 \times 8)))) \\ 46609 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + F(6) - F((0! + 9))) \\ 46610 &:= (((F(4!) + F(6)) + F(F((6 + 1)))) + 0!) \\ 46612 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times (-61))/(-2))) \\ 46613 &:= (F(4!) + ((6 + 6) + F(13))) \\ 46614 &:= (F(4!) + (6 - (6!/(1 - 4)))) \\ 46615 &:= (F(4!) + ((6 \times F(F(6))) - (-1 - 5!))) \\ 46617 &:= ((F(4!) + ((F(6) + F(6)))) + F(F((1 \times 7)))) \\ \\ 46620 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 0 \\ 46621 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 1 \\ 46622 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 2 \\ 46623 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 3 \\ 46624 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 4 \\ 46625 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 5 \\ 46626 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 6 \\ 46627 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 7 \\ 46628 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 8 \\ 46629 &:= F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times 6 \times 2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46635 &:= -((((4! - (6^6)) + F(3)) - (5))) \\ 46636 &:= ((-4) - F(6)) + ((6^{3!}) - F(6)) \\ 46638 &:= (((F(4) \times 6!) / F(6)) + F((3 \times 8))) \\ 46639 &:= -((((4! - (6^6)) + F(3)) - 9)) \\ 46641 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + ((F(6) - 4!) + 1)) \\ 46643 &:= ((-(4 - (6^6))) - F(4)) - 3! \\ 46649 &:= (((F(4) + (6^6)) + 4!) - F(9)) \\ 46650 &:= (F(F(4)) - (F(6) - (6^{5+0!}))) \\ 46658 &:= -(((4! - (((6^6) + 5))) - F(8))) \\ 46670 &:= (F(F(4)) - ((-(6^6)) - F(7)) + 0!) \\ 46675 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + F(F(6))) - (7 - 5) \\ 46676 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + F(F(6))) - (7 - 6) \\ 46677 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + F(F((6 \times 7) / 7))) \\ 46678 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + (-(6 - 7)) + F(8)) \\ 46691 &:= (F(4!) + (((6 \times 6) \times 9) - 1)) \\ 46693 &:= -((((F(4) - (6^6)) - F(9)) - 3!)) \\ 46694 &:= (F(4!) + (6 + ((6! / (-9)) \times (-4)))) \\ 46695 &:= (F((4 + 6)) \times ((6! + 9) + 5!)) \\ 46696 &:= (F(4!) + (F(6) - ((-6) - F(9)) \times F(6))) \\ 46697 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times (F(6) + F(9))) - (7))) \\ 46699 &:= (((4! / F(6))!^6) + (9 + F(9))) \\ 46703 &:= (F(4!) + (670 / F(3))) \\ 46704 &:= (F(4 \times 6) + ((F(7) + 0!) \times 4!)) \\ 46705 &:= ((F(4!) - 6) + (7^{F(-0!+5)})) \\ 46707 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + ((7! / (0! + F(7)))))) \\ 46708 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! - ((F((F(F(6)) - 7)) - F(-(0! - F(8)))))) \\ 46710 &:= (((F(4!) + (6!)) - F((F(7) + 1))) - 0!) \\ 46711 &:= (F(4!) + (6! - F((7 \times (1 + 1)))))) \\ 46712 &:= (((F(4!) + (6!)) - F((F(7) + 1))) + F(2)) \\ 46713 &:= (((F(4!) - F(6)) + F(F(7))) + ((-1 + 3!)!)) \\ 46714 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (F(7) \times (1 + 4!))) \\ 46715 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(6) - ((71 \times 5)))))) \\ 46716 &:= (((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + F((F(7) + 1))) - F(6)) \\ 46717 &:= (((F(4!) - F(F(6))) - 7) + F((1 + F(7)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46718 &:= (((F(4!) - 6) + F((F(7) + 1))) - (F(8))) \\ 46719 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + ((7 \times 1) \times 9)) \\ 46722 &:= (F(4!) + (((6! - F(7)) + F(2))/2)) \\ 46723 &:= (F(4!) + (((6 + F(7))^2) - 3!)) \\ 46724 &:= (F(4!) + (F(((6 + 7) - 2)) \times 4)) \\ 46725 &:= (((F(4!) + 6) + F(F(7))) - (2 - 5!)) \\ 46726 &:= (((F(4))!^6) + (-7) \times (-2 - F(6))) \\ 46727 &:= (F(4!) + (F(6) + (F(7) \times 27))) \\ 46728 &:= (F(4!) + ((6! + 7!)/(2 \times 8))) \\ 46730 &:= (F(4!) + (((6 + F(7))^{F(3)} + 0!)) \\ 46731 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (((7^3) - 1))) \\ 46732 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + ((7^3) \times F(2))) \\ 46733 &:= (((F(4) + F(6)) \times 7) + (3!^{3!})) \\ 46734 &:= (F(4!) + (6 + ((F(7) + F(3)) \times 4!))) \\ 46735 &:= ((F(4 \times 6) + (7)) - (-3 \times 5!)) \\ 46736 &:= ((4! + (F(6) \times 7)) + (3!^6)) \\ 46737 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(6) - F((7 \times 3) - 7)))) \\ 46738 &:= (F(4!) + ((6 + (7^3)) + F(8))) \\ 46739 &:= (F(4!) + (-((6 - (7^3))) + F(9))) \\ 46740 &:= ((-4) + F((F(F(6)) - 7))) + (F(4!) - 0!) \\ 46741 &:= ((-4) + F((F(F(6)) - 7))) + F(((4 \times 1)!)) \\ 46742 &:= (F(4!) + ((6! + ((7 \times 4))/2)) \\ 46743 &:= (F(4!) + (6! - ((7^{F(4)}) + F(3)))) \\ 46744 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(6) - ((F(7) + F(4)) \times 4!))) \\ 46745 &:= (F(4 \times 6) + (F(7) \times (4! + (5)))) \\ 46746 &:= (F(4!) + ((67 - 4) \times 6)) \\ 46747 &:= (F(4!) + (67 + (4! \times F(7)))) \\ 46748 &:= (((((F(4))! \times F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) + F(4!)) + (F(8))) \\ 46749 &:= (F(4!) + (((6! \times F(7))/4!) - 9)) \\ \\ 46750 &:= F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 0 \\ 46751 &:= F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 1 \\ 46752 &:= F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 2 \\ 46753 &:= F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 3 \\ 46754 &:= F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$46755 := F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 5$$

$$46756 := F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 6$$

$$46757 := F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 7$$

$$46758 := F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 8$$

$$46759 := F(4!) + F(F(F(6)) - 7) + 5 + 9$$

$$46760 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) \times 7) \times (F(6) - 0!)))$$

$$46761 := (((F(4))!^6) + ((F(7) \times F(6)) + 1))$$

$$46762 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (F(7) - (6!/(-2))))$$

$$46763 := ((F(4) + (F(6) \times F(7))) + (6^{3!}))$$

$$46764 := (F(4!) + (-6) \times (-((7 \times 6) - 4!)))$$

$$46764 := (F(4!) + (-6) \times (-((7 \times 6) - 4!)))$$

$$46765 := (F(4!) + ((67 \times 6) - 5))$$

$$46766 := ((F(4))! + ((F(6) \times F(7)) + (6^6)))$$

$$46767 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) + F(7)) \times (6 + F(7))))$$

$$46768 := (F(4!) + (F(6) \times ((7 \times 6) + 8)))$$

$$46769 := (((F(4))!^6) + ((F(7) \times F(6)) + 9))$$

$$46770 := (F(4!) + (-67) \times (-7 + 0!))$$

$$46773 := (F(4!) + (6! - (7!/(F(7) + 3))))$$

$$46774 := (((F(F(4)) + (F(6) \times 7)) \times 7) + F(4!))$$

$$46775 := (((F(4))!^6) + (-((7/7) + 5!))$$

$$46776 := -((4! + (((-6) \times F(7)) + F(7)) \times 6!))$$

$$46782 := (F(4!) + (-6) \times (F(7) - (82)))$$

$$46783 := (F(4!) + ((F(6) - F(7)) \times (-83)))$$

$$46785 := ((4! - ((6! \times F(7)) + F(8))) \times (-5))$$

$$46786 := ((F((F(4))!))! - (((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) + (8!/(-6))))$$

$$46787 := ((F(F(4)) \times 6!) - ((F(7) - 8!) - 7!))$$

$$46788 := (F(4!) + (6 \times (78 - 8)))$$

$$46789 := ((F(4!) + F((F(6) + (7)))) + (F(8) \times (-9)))$$

$$46790 := ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + (((F(7) \times F(9)) + 0!)))$$

$$46791 := (F(4!) + (-6) + (F(7) \times (F(9) - 1)))$$

$$46792 := (F(4!) + (F(6) + (F(7) \times (F(9) - 2))))$$

$$46793 := (((F(4))!^6) + (-7) + F((9 + 3)))$$

$$46794 := (F(4!) + (F(6) + ((F(7) \times F(9)) - 4!)))$$

$$46795 := ((F(F(4)) \times 6!) + ((7! \times 9) - (5)))$$

$$46796 := (-4) + (((F(6) \times 7) + 9) \times 6!))$$

$$46798 := (((F(4!) + F(6)) + F(F(7))) + (9 \times F(8)))$$

$$46799 := (F(4!) + (F(6) + ((F(7) + F(9)) \times 9)))$$

$$46800 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 0$$

$$46801 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 1$$

$$46802 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 2$$

$$46803 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 3$$

$$46804 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 4$$

$$46805 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 5$$

$$46806 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 6$$

$$46807 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 7$$

$$46808 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 8$$

$$46809 := F(4)!! \times (F(6) \times 8 + 0!) + 9$$

$$46810 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 0$$

$$46811 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 1$$

$$46812 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 2$$

$$46813 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 3$$

$$46814 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 4$$

$$46815 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 5$$

$$46816 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 6$$

$$46817 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 7$$

$$46818 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 8$$

$$46819 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) \times F(8) + 1 + 9$$

$$46821 := (F(F((F(4)!)) + (6! \times ((8^2) + 1)))$$

$$46822 := (F(4!) - ((F(6) + (F(8) \times (-22))))))$$

$$46823 := (F(4!) + (F(6) + ((F(8)^2) + 3!)))$$

$$46824 := (F(4 \times 6) + ((F(8) - 2) \times 4!))$$

$$46825 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + ((F(8)^2) - (5)))$$

$$46826 := (((F(4)^{F(6)}) + 8!) - F((2 + F(6))))$$

$$46827 := (F(4!) + ((F(-((F(6) - F(8)))) \times 2) - 7))$$

$$46828 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + (-2 + F(8))))$$

$$46829 := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (8 \times F((F(2) + 9))))$$

$$46830 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 0$$

$$46831 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 1$$

$$46832 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 2$$

$$46833 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 3$$

$$46834 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 4$$

$$46835 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 5$$

$$46836 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 6$$

$$46837 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 7$$

$$46838 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 8$$

$$46839 := F(4!) + F(F(6)) + F(8)^{F(3)} + 9$$

$$46840 := (((F(4))!^6) + (8 \times (4! - 0!)))$$

$$46842 := (F(4!) - ((F(-((F(6) - F(8)))) + 4) \times (-2)))$$

$$46843 := (((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + ((F(8) \times 4!))) - F(3!))$$

$$46844 := (F(4!) + (-(68) \times (-4) - F(4)))$$

$$46845 := (F(4!) + (6! - (F((8 - 4)^5)))$$

$$46846 := (((4!)! / (F(F(6)))!) - (((F(F(8)) - F(4!)) + (6!))))$$

$$46847 := (((F(4)^{F(6)} + 8!) - F((-4) + F(7)))$$

$$46848 := (((F(4)^6 \times (-8)) - 4!) \times (-8))$$

$$46849 := (F(4!) - (((F(6) - F(8)) \times (F(4) + F(9))))$$

$$46851 := ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + ((F(8) \times ((5 - 1)!)))$$

$$46852 := (F(4!) + (((6 + F(8)) - (5))^2))$$

$$46853 := (F(4!) + ((6! - F((8 + 5))) - F(3)))$$

$$46854 := (F(4!) + (6 \times ((8 - 5)^4)))$$

$$46855 := (F(4!) - ((F(6) - ((F(8) - 5!) \times (-5))))$$

$$46856 := (F(4!) + (F(6) \times (F(8) + (5 \times F(6))))$$

$$46857 := ((F(4!) + (6! + F((8 - 5)))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$46859 := ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + ((F((8 - 5))^9)))$$

$$46860 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 0$$

$$46861 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 1$$

$$46862 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 2$$

$$46863 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 3$$

$$46864 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 4$$

$$46865 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 5$$

$$46866 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 6$$

$$46867 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 7$$

$$46868 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 8$$

$$46869 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! - F(F(6)) + 9$$

$$46871 := ((F(4!) - (-6) \times F(8))) + F((F(7) + 1)))$$

$$46872 := (((F(4)^{F(6)} + 8!) - (7 + 2))$$

$$46873 := (((F(4)^{F(6)} + 8!) - (7)) - F(F(3)))$$

$$46874 := (F(4!) - ((6 - (8^{7-4}))))$$

$$46875 := (F(4!) + ((F(6)^{F(8)/7} - (5)))$$

$$46876 := (((F(4)^{F(6)} + 8!) - F(7)) + F(6))$$

$$46877 := (F(4!) + ((6 \times 87) - F(7)))$$

$$46878 := ((F(4)^{F(6)} - ((F(8)/7) - 8!))$$

$$46879 := (((F(4)^{F(6)} + 8!) + ((7 - 9)))$$

$$46880 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 0$$

$$46881 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 1$$

$$46882 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 2$$

$$46883 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 3$$

$$46884 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 4$$

$$46885 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 5$$

$$46886 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 6$$

$$46887 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 7$$

$$46888 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 8$$

$$46889 := F(4!) + F(6) \times 8 \times 8 + 9$$

$$46890 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 0$$

$$46891 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 1$$

$$46892 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 2$$

$$46893 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 3$$

$$46894 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 4$$

$$46895 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 5$$

$$46896 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 6$$

$$46897 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 7$$

$$46898 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 8$$

$$46899 := F(4)^{F(6)} + 8! + 9 + 9$$

$$46902 := (F(4!) + (6 \times F((9 + 02))))$$

$$46904 := (F(4!) + ((6 \times 90) - 4))$$

$$46905 := ((4! + (F(6))!) + (9^{-0!+5}))$$

$$46908 := (F(4!) + (6! - (-9) \times (0! - F(8))))$$

$$46912 := (F(4!) + ((6 \times 91) - 2))$$

$$46913 := ((F(4!) + (6 \times 91)) - F(F(3)))$$

$$46914 := ((F(F(4)) \times ((F(6) \times F(9)) + 1)) + F(4!))$$

$$46915 := (((F(4)^{F(6)} + F(9)) + (F((1 + 5))))!)$$

$$46916 := (((((F(4)^{F(6)} + F(9)) + 1) + (F(6))!))$$

$$46920 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 0$$

$$46921 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 1$$

$$46922 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 2$$

$$46923 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 3$$

$$46924 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 4$$

$$46925 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 5$$

$$46926 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 6$$

$$46927 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 7$$

$$46928 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 8$$

$$46929 := F(4!) + 6 \times 92 + 9$$

$$46932 := (F(4!) + (-6) \times (-93 - F(2)))$$

$$46933 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(6)) \times (9 \times 3)) - F(3)))$$

$$46934 := ((F(4!) + (6! - F(9))) - ((F(3) + F(4))))!$$

$$46935 := (((F(4!) + (6! - F(9))) + F(F(3))) - 5!)$$

$$46936 := (F(4!) + ((69 + F(3)) \times F(6)))$$

$$46937 := (F(4!) + ((6! - F((9 + 3))) - (7)))$$

$$46938 := (F(4!) + ((6 + 9) \times 38))$$

$$46939 := (F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - 39))$$

$$46940 := (F(4!) + (-((F(6) - F(9))) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) + 0!)))$$

- 46941** := (((F((F(4)))!)! - F((F(F(6)) - 9))) + F((F(F((F(4)))!) - 1)))
- 46942** := ((F(4!) - F(-((6 - 9)))) + (4!²))
- 46943** := (F(4!) + ((F(6) - 9) + (4!^{F(3)})))
- 46946** := (F(4!) + ((F((6 + 9)) - 4!) - F(6)))
- 46947** := (F(4!) + ((F((6 + 9)) - 4!) - (7)))
- 46948** := ((F(4!) - F(6)) + ((F(9) - (F(4))!) × F(8)))
- 46949** := ((F(4!) + (69)) + (F(F(4))⁹))
- 46952** := (F(4!) + (F(6) + (((9 - 5))!²)))
- 46953** := -((F(4) × ((F(6) - F(9)) - (5^{3!}))))
- 46954** := (F(4!) + ((6! - 9) - (5^{F(4)})))
- 46955** := ((F(4!) + F(F(6))) - ((F(9) + (5! × (-5))))))
- 46956** := (F(4!) + (-6) × (-9) - F((5 + 6)))
- 46957** := ((F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)))) - F((-5) + F(7)))
- 46959** := (F(4!) + ((6! - (95)) - F(9)))
- 46962** := (F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - (F(6) × 2)))
- 46963** := ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + (F((9 + 6)) + 3!))
- 46964** := ((F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - F(6))) - (F(4))!)
- 46964** := ((F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - F(6))) - (F(4))!)
- 46965** := (F(4!) + ((6! - F(9)) - F((6 + 5))))
- 46966** := (F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - (6 + 6)))
- 46968** := (F(4!) + ((69 + 6) × 8))
- 46970** := (F(4!) + ((F((6 + 9)) - (7)) - 0!))
- 46971** := (F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - (7 × 1)))
- 46972** := (F(4!) + ((F((6 + 9)) - (7)) + F(2)))
- 46973** := (F(4!) + ((F((6 + 9)) - (7)) + F(3)))
- 46974** := (F(4!) + (6 × (97 + 4)))
- 46975** := (((((F(4))!⁶) - F(9)) + F(F(7))) + 5!)
- 46976** := (F(4!) + ((69 + 7) × F(6)))
- 46977** := (F(4!) + ((6! - F(9)) - 77))
- 46978** := (((F(4)^{F(6)}) + 97) + 8!)
- 46979** := ((F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)))) + F(-((7 - 9))))
- 46982** := (F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) + (8/2)))
- 46983** := (F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) + (8 - 3)))
- 46984** := (F(4!) + (((6!/(-9)) × (-8)) - 4!))

- 46985 := (F(4!) + (6! - ((98 + 5))))
 46986 := (F(4!) + (6! - (((9 + 8) × 6))))
 46989 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(6)) × (9 + F(8))) - 9))
 46990 := (F(4!) + ((69 × 9) + 0!))
 46991 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(6)) × F(9)) - (91)))
 46992 := (F(4!) + ((-6) - (9 × F(9))) × (-2))
 46994 := ((F(4!) + ((-((6 - 9)))!)) - 94)
 46996 := (((F(4!) × (-6! - 9!))/9!) + (6!))
 46998 := (F(4!) + (((6 + (9/9)))!/8))
 46999 := (F(4!) + (6! - F((99/9))))
 47024 := ((F(4!) + ((7 - 0!)!) - (2^{F(4!)}))
 47027 := (((F((F(4)!))! × (-7))/(-(0! + 2)!)) - F(7))
 47028 := (F(4!) + ((F(7) - 0!) × F((2 + 8))))
 47033 := ((F(4!) - F((7 + 03))) + 3!!)
 47034 := -((((F((F(4) + (7))) - 0!) - 3!!) - F(4!)))
 47035 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((7 + 0!)!/3!) - (5)))
 47036 := (F(4!) - (((F(7) × (0! + 3)) - 6!)))
 47037 := (-F(4) + (((7 + 0!)!/(-3!)) × (-7)))
 47038 := -((F(F(4)) - (((7 + 0!)!/3!) + 8!))
 47040 := ((F((F(4)!))! - (((7 + 0!)!/(F(4)!)) × (-0!)))
 47041 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((7 + 0!)!/(F(4)!)) + 1))
 47042 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((7 + 0!)!/(F(4)!)) + 2))
 47043 := (((F(4!) - F((7 + 0!))) - (4!)) + 3!!)
 47044 := ((F(4!) + ((7 - 0!)!) - 44)
 47045 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((7 + 0!)!/(F(4)!)) + (5)))
 47046 := (F(4!) - (((F(7) + 0!) × F(4)) - 6!))
 47047 := (((F(4)! + ((7 + 0!)!)/(F(4)!)) × 7)
 47048 := (F((F(4)!)) × (-((7! + 0!) + 4!)) + F(F(8)))
 47049 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((7 + 0!)!/(F(4)!)) + 9))
 47053 := ((F(4!) - (7 × 05)) + 3!!)
 47054 := ((F(4!) + ((7 - 0!)!) - F((5 + 4)))
 47056 := (F((F(4)!)) × ((-7!) - (-((0! - (5))))!) + F(F(F(6))))
 47059 := ((F(4!) + ((7 - 0!)!) + (5 - F(9)))
 47061 := ((-4!) + ((7 + 0!)!) + F((F(F(6)) - 1)))
 47063 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + ((0! + F(F(6))) × F(F(3!))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 47064 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times 0) + 6)!) - 4!) \\
 47065 &:= (((F(4!)/7) + 0!) + (F(6)!) + 5!) \\
 47066 &:= (F(4!) + (706 - F(6))) \\
 47067 &:= (F(4!) + (706 - 7)) \\
 47068 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times 0)!) + 6!) - F(8)) \\
 47069 &:= ((F(4!) - F(7)) + (F(F(06)) \times F(9))) \\
 47072 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (-F(7)) + F((-0!) + F((7 + F(2)))))) \\
 47073 &:= (F(4!) + (707 - F(3))) \\
 47074 &:= ((F(4!) - (F(7) + 0!)) + (((7 - 4)!)!) \\
 47074 &:= ((F(4!) - (F(7) + 0!)) + (((7 - 4)!)!) \\
 47075 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(7) + ((0! - (7)) \times 5!))) \\
 47076 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times 0)!) - F(7)) + 6!) \\
 47077 &:= ((F((F(4)!) \times (7! - 0!)) + F((F(7) + (7)))) \\
 47078 &:= (F((F(4) \times 7) - 0!)) - (7 - 8!) \\
 47079 &:= (F(4!) + ((7!/07) - 9)) \\
 \\
 47080 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 0 \\
 47081 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 1 \\
 47082 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 2 \\
 47083 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 3 \\
 47084 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 4 \\
 47085 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 5 \\
 47086 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 6 \\
 47087 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 7 \\
 47088 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 8 \\
 47089 &:= F(4!) + (7 - 0!)! - 8 + 9 \\
 \\
 47092 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!) + (7 + F(((0! + 9) \times 2)))) \\
 47093 &:= ((F(4!) + ((F(7) + 0!) - 9)) + 3!) \\
 47094 &:= ((F(4!) + (7 - 0!)) + ((9 - F(4))!) \\
 47095 &:= ((F(4!) + 7) + (((0 \times 9)!) + (5))!) \\
 47096 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 + ((0 \times 9)!) + 6!)) \\
 47097 &:= ((F(4)^{7-0!}) + F((-9 + F(7))!)) \\
 47098 &:= (F(4!) + (709 + F(8))) \\
 47101 &:= ((F(4!) + F(7)) + (((1 + 0!) + 1)!)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 47102** := $((F(4!) + (F(7) + 1)) + (((0! + 2))!))!$
47103 := $((F(4!) + ((F(7) + 1) + 0!)) + 3!!)$
47104 := $(F(F((F(4))!)) + ((F(7) \times F(10)) + F(4!)))$
47106 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (F((F((7 + 1)) - 0!)) + F(F(6))))$
47108 := $(F(4!) + (((7 - 1))! - 0!) + F(8))$
47109 := $((F(4!) + (((7 - 1))!)) + F(-(0! - 9)))$
47114 := $((F(4))! + ((F(7) \times (1 + 1)) + F(4!)))$
47119 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((F((F((7 + 1)) - 1)) + F(9))))$
47121 := $(F(4!) + ((F((F(7) + 1)) \times 2) - 1))$
47122 := $(F(4!) + (F(((7 \times 1) \times 2)) \times 2))$
47123 := $((F(4!) + (7!/F(12))) + 3!!)$
47124 := $((F(F(4)) \times F((F(7) + 1))) + 2) + F(4!))$
47129 := $((F(4!) + 7) + (((1 + 2))!)) + F(9)$
47133 := $(F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) + 1) + F(F(3!))) \times 3))$
47134 := $((47 - 1) + 3!!) + F(4!))$
47136 := $(F(4!) + (((7 + 1) \times 3!) + 6!))$
47138 := $((F(4!) + (71)) + 3!!) - (F(8))$
47143 := $((F(4!) + (((7 - 1))!)) + F((4 + 3!)))$
47144 := $((F(4))! + (((F(7) + 1) \times 4) + F(4!)))$
47145 := $(F(4!) + (7 \times ((-1 - F((F(4))!)) + 5!)))$
47146 := $(F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) - 1)/4) + (6!)))$
47149 := $(F(4!) + (71 \times (F(F(4)) + 9)))$
47152 := $(F(4!) + (-((7 \times (1 - 5))^2))$
47153 := $((F(4!) + (F(7) \times (1 \times 5))) + 3!!)$
47154 := $((F(4))! + ((71 - 5) + F(4!)))$
47159 := $((F(4))! + (71)) + F(-(5 - 9))!))$
47160 := $(F(4!) + ((71 + 6!) + 0!))$
47161 := $(F(4!) + (F(7) \times (1 \times 61)))$
47163 := $((F(4))! \times F(7)) + F((-1 + F(F(6)))) + (F(3))!)$
47164 := $(F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - F((1 + F(6)))) \times 4))$
47166 := $(F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (1 \times 6)) + 6!))$
47173 := $(F(4!) + ((F(7) + F(17))/F(3)))$
47176 := $((F(4!)/7) - 1) + F(F(7)) + (F(6))!$
47177 := $((F(4!)/7) + ((1 + 7))! + F(F(7)))$
47178 := $((F(4!)/7) + 1) + F(F(7)) + 8!$

$$\begin{aligned}47179 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (17 \times F(9))) \\47184 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7) + F((1 \times 8))) \times 4!)) \\47186 &:= ((F(4!) + F((F(7) + 1))) - (-F(8) \times F(F(6)))) \\47187 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) \times ((1 + 8) \times 7))) \\47188 &:= (4 \times ((7! + F((-1 + F(8)))) - 8)) \\47193 &:= ((F(4!) + (71 + F(9))) + 3!!) \\47196 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(7) - 1) \times 9) + 6!)) \\47197 &:= ((F(4!) - F(7)) + (F(F(-(1 - 9))))/F(7)) \\47204 &:= (((-4) + 7!) + F(20)) \times 4 \\47205 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times 7!) + (F(20) + 5!)) \\47207 &:= ((4 \times (7! + F(20))) - F(7)) \\47208 &:= (F(4!) + (7!/(-2 - 08))) \\47210 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4)!)))/F(7)) + (F(((2 + 1) + 0!))!)) \\47213 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7)^2) \times (-1 + 3!)) \\47214 &:= (((F(4)! + (7!/((2 + 1)!))) + F(4!)) \\47215 &:= (F(4!) + (-7) \times (-((2 - 1) - 5!)) \\47216 &:= (((-4) - 7!) + F(21)) \times F(6) \\47217 &:= (F(4!) + (7 + (F(21)/F(7))) \\47220 &:= (4 \times ((7! \times F(2)) + F(20))) \\47224 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4)!)) - (7! + F((2 + 2)))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\47226 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) \times (2 + (2^6)))) \\47227 &:= ((F(4!) + (7!)) - F((-2) + F((F(2) + (7)))))) \\47228 &:= ((F(4!) + (7! + F(2))) - F((-2) + F(8))) \\47229 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (7 \times F(-((2 - (2 \times 9)))))) \\47230 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((7 \times F((2 \times F(3)))) + 0!)) \\47231 &:= (((F(4!) + F((F(7) - F(2)))) + 3!!) - 1) \\47232 &:= (F(4!) + ((72 \times 3!) \times 2)) \\47233 &:= (((F(4!) + F((F(7) - F(2)))) + F(F(3))) + 3!!) \\47234 &:= ((F(4!) + (7! \times (-2))) + F((-3) + 4!)) \\47235 &:= (F(4) \times (((7 - 2)^{3!}) + 5!)) \\47236 &:= (((F(4!) + (F(7)^2)) + 3!!) - F(F(6))) \\47238 &:= ((F(4!) - (((7! - 2) \times F(3)))) + F(F(8))) \\47239 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(7) \times (F(2) - (F(3) \times F(9)))))) \\47240 &:= F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 0\end{aligned}$$

$$47241 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 1$$

$$47242 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 2$$

$$47243 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 3$$

$$47244 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 4$$

$$47245 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 5$$

$$47246 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 6$$

$$47247 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 7$$

$$47248 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 8$$

$$47249 := F(F(4)!) \times (-7! - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 9$$

$$47253 := (((F((F(4))!) \times F((7 + F(2)))) + (5)) - (F(3)!))!$$

$$47254 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(7)^2) + F((5 \times 4))))$$

$$47255 := (((F(4))! + 7) \times (F((2 + 5)) \times 5))$$

$$47256 := (F(4!) + ((-(7 + 2)) + 5!) \times F(6))$$

$$47257 := (F(4!) + (((7 \times F(2)) + 5!) \times 7))$$

$$47259 := (F(4!) + ((F((7 + F(2))) - 5!) \times (-9)))$$

$$47262 := ((F((F(4))!) \times (-(7! - 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 2)$$

$$47263 := (F(4!) + (((F(7)^2) + 6!) + 3!))$$

$$47264 := (F(4!) + ((7 \times 2) \times 64))$$

$$47265 := (F(4!) + (F(7) \times ((2^6) + 5)))$$

$$47266 := (F((4! - (7 + 2))) + (6^6))$$

$$47268 := (4 + ((-(7! - 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8)$$

$$47271 := (F(4!) + (7 \times ((2^7) + 1)))$$

$$47273 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (F(F(7)) - (((F(2) + (7))!)/(-3!))))$$

$$47274 := (((4 \times F(F(7))) - (2 \times F(7))) + F(4!))$$

$$47274 := (((4 \times F(F(7))) - (2 \times F(7))) + F(4!))$$

$$47276 := ((F((F(4))!) - (F(F(7)) - 2)) \times (-(F(F(7)) - F(F(6))))$$

$$47277 := (F(4!) + (F(7) + ((2^7) \times 7)))$$

$$47279 := (F(4!) + (-7) + (27 \times F(9)))$$

$$47282 := (((4! - 7!) + F((2 + F(8)))) \times 2)$$

$$47283 := ((F(4!) - (72)) + F((8 \times F(3))))$$

$$47284 := (((4 \times F(F(7))) - (2 \times 8)) + F(4!))$$

$$47286 := (F(4!) + (F((7 + 2)) \times (F(8) + (6))))$$

$$47287 := (((-4) \times ((F(7) - F(2))!)/(-8!)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$47288 := ((4! + F(F(7))) \times ((2 + F(8)) \times 8))$$

$$\begin{aligned}47292 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) + ((F(2) + (F(9)^2)))) \\47293 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) + (2 + (F(9)^{F(3)}))) \\47294 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times ((7 - 2)!)) + (-(F(9)) + F(4!))) \\47300 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 0 \\47301 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 1 \\47302 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 2 \\47303 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 3 \\47304 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 4 \\47305 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 5 \\47306 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 6 \\47307 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 7 \\47308 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 8 \\47309 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times (3 + 0!) + 9 \\47310 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(F(7)) \times (3 \times 10))) \\47312 &:= (F(4!) + (7! - (F(3)^{12}))) \\47313 &:= (((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + 3!) - F((1 \times 3)!)) \\47314 &:= (((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + 3!) - 1) - (F(4)!) \\47315 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (3! \times (-1 + 5!))) \\47316 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (-3)) + F(16))) \\47317 &:= (F(4!) + (73 \times F((1 \times 7)))) \\47318 &:= ((F(((F(4)! + 7)) + (F(3)!))!) + (F((-1 + F(8)))))) \\47319 &:= (-(F(F(4))) + ((7 \times F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) - F(9))) \\47320 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (((3 \times 2)! - 0!)) \\47321 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (((3 + 2) + 1)!)) \\47322 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (((3 \times 2)! + F(2))) \\47323 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (F(3) + ((2 \times 3)!)) \\47324 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (3 + ((2 + 4)!)) \\47325 &:= (((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + 3!) - ((F(2) - (5)))) \\47326 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 \times F((3^2))) + 6!)) \\47328 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 + 3)/2)! \times 8)) \\47329 &:= (((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + 3!) - ((F(2) - 9))) \\47330 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^3! + 0\end{aligned}$$

$$47331 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 1$$

$$47332 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 2$$

$$47333 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 3$$

$$47334 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 4$$

$$47335 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 5$$

$$47336 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 6$$

$$47337 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 7$$

$$47338 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 8$$

$$47339 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) + 3^{3!} + 9$$

$$47340 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + (((F(7)!)/(F(3)!)))/(F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!)))$$

$$47341 := (((F(4!) - F(7)) + F((F(3)^4))) - 1)$$

$$47342 := (F(4!) + ((-7) - 3!) + F((4^2)))$$

$$47343 := (F(4!) + (F(7) \times ((3 \times 4!) + 3)))$$

$$47344 := (F(4!) + (((7 + 3)^{F(4)}) - 4!))$$

$$47346 := ((F(4!) - (7 + F(3))) + F((4! - F(6))))$$

$$47347 := (F(4!) + ((F(7) - F(3)) \times F((4 + 7))))$$

$$47348 := ((F(4!) - 7) + F((F(3)^{-4+8})))$$

$$47349 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) - (((F(3) - 4!) \times F(9))))$$

$$47350 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 0$$

$$47351 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 1$$

$$47352 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 2$$

$$47353 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 3$$

$$47354 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 4$$

$$47355 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 5$$

$$47356 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 6$$

$$47357 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 7$$

$$47358 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 8$$

$$47359 := F(4!) + F(F(7) + 3) - 5 + 9$$

$$47360 := ((F(4!) + F((F(7) + 3))) + (6 - 0!))$$

$$47361 := ((F(4!) + F((F(7) + 3))) + (6 \times 1))$$

$$47362 := (F(4!) + (7 + F(((3 \times 6) - 2))))$$

$$47363 := (((F(4) \times F(F(7))) + F(3!)) + (6^{3!}))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47364 &:= (F(4!) + ((-7) + (F(3)^{F(6)})) \times 4)) \\ 47366 &:= ((F(4) - F(7)) + ((3!^6) + 6!)) \\ 47367 &:= -((F(F(4)) - ((-F(7)) + 3!!) \times 67))) \\ 47368 &:= (F(4!) + ((7!/(-3) + F(6))) - 8)) \\ 47369 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) \times (-3) - (6!/(-9)))) \\ 47373 &:= (F(4!) - (((7!/(F(3) - (7))) + 3))) \\ 47374 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(7) + 3!)) + F((F(7) + F(4)))) \\ 47374 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(7) + 3!)) + F((F(7) + F(4)))) \\ 47375 &:= (F(4!) + (((7! + F(3)) - (7))/5)) \\ 47376 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 - 3))! \times (7 \times 6))) \\ 47377 &:= (F(4!) + ((7!/3!) + (F(7) \times F(7)))) \\ 47378 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (37 \times F(8))) \\ 47379 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 - 3))! + F((7 + 9)))) \\ 47380 &:= (4 + (7 \times (3 + F((F(8) - 0!)))) \\ 47381 &:= -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (-7) + ((3!)! \times (-81)))) \\ 47382 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7)^{F(3)}) \times (8 - 2))) \\ 47383 &:= (((F(4)^{7+3}) - F(F(8))) - 3!!) \\ 47384 &:= (((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + 3!!) + (F(8) \times F(4))) \\ 47385 &:= ((F(4!) - 7) + (F(3!) \times (8 + 5!))) \\ 47386 &:= (((F(4))!)! - ((F(7)^{F(3)})) \times 86) \\ 47390 &:= ((F(4!) + F((F(7) + 3))) + (F(9) + 0!)) \\ 47392 &:= (F(4!) + ((-((7 - 39))^2))) \\ 47393 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + ((F(3!) \times 9) + 3!!)) \\ 47394 &:= ((F(4!) - ((7! - F(3)) \times 9)) + F(4!)) \\ 47395 &:= (F(4!) + (7 + ((3! \times F(9)) \times 5))) \\ 47396 &:= ((-4) - (F(F(7)) \times (-3!)) \times F((9!/(F(6))!))) \\ 47397 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 \times 3!) + F((9 + 7)))) \\ 47398 &:= -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(7) \times (((F(3))!)/9) + 8))) \\ 47399 &:= (F(4!) + (((-F(7)) \times (3!)!)/(-9) - 9)) \\ 47403 &:= ((F(4))! + (7 \times ((F(4))! + F((-0!) + F(F(3!))))) \\ 47404 &:= ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times (7 + F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!))))/F(4)) \\ 47405 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) + (4^05))) \\ 47406 &:= ((F(4))! \times ((F(F(7)) \times F((F((F(4))! + 0!))) - (F(F(6)))))) \\ 47407 &:= (F(4) + ((-7) - F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!))) \times (-7)) \end{aligned}$$

- 47408** := $(F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (-4)) \times (0! - F(8))))$
47410 := $((F(4!) + F((F(7) + F(4)))) + (F(10)))$
47413 := $((F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (4! + 1)))) + 3!!)$
47414 := $(F(4) + (7 \times (F((F(4))!) + F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!))))))$
47416 := $(F((F(4))!) \times ((-7!) + F(F(((4 - 1)!))) + F(F(F(6))))))$
47417 := $((((F((F(4))!)! \times (-7)) / (-F(4))!) + (F((1 + F(7))))))$
47418 := $(F(4!) + (((7^{F(4)}) + 1) \times F(8)))$
47419 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (7 \times (F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 1)) + 9)))$
47423 := $(-F(F(F(4))) + (F(7) \times ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - 2) / 3)))$
47424 := $(((4^7) - (4!^2)) \times F(4))$
47426 := $(F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (4! + 2)) + 6!))$
47428 := $((F((F(4))!)! - ((7^{F(4)}) - F(-(F(2) - F(8))))))$
47430 := $((((F(4!) + ((7^{F(4)}))) + 3!!) - 0!)$
47431 := $((F(4!) + ((7^{F(4)}))) + (((3 \times 1))!))$
47432 := $((((4! \times F(7)) - (4))^{F(3)}) / 2)$
47433 := $((F(4!) + ((7^{F(4)} + F(3))) + 3!!)$
47434 := $((F(4!) - F(F(7))) + ((F(4) + (3!^4))))$
47435 := $(F(4!) - ((F(7) - ((F(4)^{F(3)} \times 5!))))$
47436 := $(F(4!) + ((F((7 + 4)) \times F(3)) \times 6))$
47437 := $((F(4!) + ((7! - 4!) / 3!)) + F(F(7)))$
47438 := $((F(4!) + (7! / F(4))) - F(-(3! - F(8))))$
47439 := $(F(4!) + (7 \times (F((4 \times 3)) + 9)))$
- 47440** := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 0$
47441 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 1$
47442 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 2$
47443 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 3$
47444 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 4$
47445 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 5$
47446 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 6$
47447 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 7$
47448 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 8$
47449 := $F(F(4))! \times (-7! + 4! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + 9$
- 47450** := $((((F(4))!)! + (F(F(7)) - 4)) \times 50)$

$$47453 := ((4 + (-F(7)) \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (5)))) / (-3))$$

$$47454 := (((F(4))! + (((F(7) - 4) \times 5!))) + F(4!))$$

$$47455 := (F(4!) + (7 + ((4 + 5) \times 5!))$$

$$47456 := (F(4!) + (((F(7) + F(4)) + 5!) \times F(6)))$$

$$47457 := ((-4) + F(7)) \times (((F(F(4)) + (5)))! + F(F(7)))$$

$$47459 := (F(4!) + ((7 + 4) + (5! \times 9)))$$

$$47460 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 0$$

$$47461 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 1$$

$$47462 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 2$$

$$47463 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 3$$

$$47464 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 4$$

$$47465 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 5$$

$$47466 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 6$$

$$47467 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 7$$

$$47468 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 8$$

$$47469 := F(4!) + F(7) \times 4 \times F(F(6)) + 9$$

$$47472 := (F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) \times 4!) - (7!)) \times 2))$$

$$47473 := (F(4!) + (((F(7)^{F(4)}) + F(7)) / F(3)))$$

$$47474 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F((F(7) + (F(4))!))) - 7) - (F((F(4))!))!)$$

$$47474 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F((F(7) + (F(4))!))) - 7) - (F((F(4))!))!)$$

$$47475 := ((F(4!) + F((F(7) - ((4 - 7)))))) + 5!$$

$$47478 := (F(4!) + (74 \times (7 + 8)))$$

$$47479 := (4 + (((-7!) - F(F(4))) - F(F(7))) \times (-9))$$

$$47480 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F((F(7) + (F(4))!))) - (8! + 0!))$$

$$47481 := (F(4) \times (-F(7)) - (((F(4))! \times (-F(8) + 1))))$$

$$47482 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F((F(7) + (F(4))!))) - ((8! - F(2))))$$

$$47483 := (((F(F(4))^7) + F(4!)) + F((8 \times F(3))))$$

$$47484 := (F(4!) + ((7! / 4) - F((8 + 4))))$$

$$47485 := (F(((F(4))! + F(7))) + (4 \times (F(F(8)) - 5!)))$$

$$47486 := (F(4!) - ((F(7) - (F(4) \times F((8 + 6))))))$$

$$47487 := (F(4!) + (((F(7)^{F(4)}) \times 8) - F(F(7))))$$

$$47488 := (((F(4))! - ((7! - 4!))) + F(F(8))) \times 8$$

$$47489 := (((F(4) \times (7^4)) + 8!) - F(9))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47490 &:= (F(4!) + (F((F(7) - (4))) \times (F(9) - 0!))) \\ 47493 &:= (F(4!) + ((-7) - 4!) + (F(9)^{F(3)})) \\ 47495 &:= ((47 + F(4!)) + (9 \times 5!)) \\ 47496 &:= ((4! \times F((7 + 4))) + (9!/F(6))) \\ 47497 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (4 \times (-9) + F(F(7)))) \\ 47498 &:= (((F(4)!) \times F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times F((9!/8!)) \\ 47499 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) \times (-4 - 9)) - F(9))) \\ 47502 &:= (F((F(F(4)) \times 7)) \times (5! + ((0! + 2)!)) \\ 47503 &:= (((F(4)!) - F(F(7))) \times (-5)) + F(((0! + 3)!)) \\ 47504 &:= (((F(4)!) - F(F(7))) \times (-5) + 0!) + F(4!) \\ 47507 &:= (((F(4)!) \times ((F(7) \times 5) + 0!)) - F(7)) \\ 47512 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(F(7)) \times 5)) - F(F(((1 + 2)!))) \\ 47513 &:= (((-4) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + F(((1 + 3)!)) \\ 47514 &:= (((-4) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + 1) + F(4!) \\ 47515 &:= (((F(4)!) \times ((F(7) \times 5) + 1)) - (5)) \\ 47516 &:= (-4) - (((F(7) \times (-5)) - 1) \times 6!) \\ \\ 47520 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 0 \\ 47521 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 1 \\ 47522 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 2 \\ 47523 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 3 \\ 47524 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 4 \\ 47525 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 5 \\ 47526 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 6 \\ 47527 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 7 \\ 47528 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 8 \\ 47529 &:= F(4)!! \times (F(7) \times 5 + F(2)) + 9 \\ \\ 47530 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 0 \\ 47531 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 1 \\ 47532 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 2 \\ 47533 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 3 \\ 47534 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 4 \\ 47535 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 5 \\ 47536 &:= F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$47537 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 7$$

$$47538 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 8$$

$$47539 := F(4!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 - 3 + 9$$

$$47540 := (F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) \times 5) + (F(4)!) + 0!))$$

$$47541 := (((F(4)^7) - 5!) \times (4! - 1))$$

$$47542 := (((((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + F(4!)) - F(2))$$

$$47543 := (((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + F((4 \times 3!)))$$

$$47544 := (F(4!) + (7 \times ((5! + 4!) + 4!)))$$

$$47545 := (F(4!) + (-((F(7) - 5!) \times ((F(4)!) + (5))))$$

$$47546 := (((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + ((F(4!) + F(6))))$$

$$47547 := ((F(4)^7) + ((5 + 4) \times 7!))$$

$$47553 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) \times 5) + (5!/3!)))$$

$$47554 := ((F(F(4)) \times (-7 - (5! \times (-5)))) + F(4!))$$

$$47555 := (F(4!) - ((F(7) - (5! \times (5 + 5))))$$

$$47556 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (-5) + (5! \times F(6)))$$

$$47560 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + ((5! \times F(6)) - 0!))$$

$$47561 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) - ((5! \times F(6)) \times (-1)))$$

$$47562 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + ((5! \times F(6)) + F(2)))$$

$$47563 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (((5! \times F(6)) + F(3))))$$

$$47564 := (F(4!) + (F(7) \times (F((5 + 6)) + F(4))))$$

$$47567 := (((((F(4)!) \times F(7)) \times F((5!/F(6)))) - F(7))$$

$$47568 := (F(4!) + ((F((7 + 5)) + (6)) \times 8))$$

$$47569 := (-4!) + (7 \times (F((5!/6)) + F(9)))$$

$$47573 := (((F((F(4)!) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + F(((7 - 3)!))$$

$$47574 := (F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + ((5^{(7-4)!})))$$

$$47574 := (F(4) \times (F(F(7)) + ((5^{(7-4)!})))$$

$$47575 := ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) - (5! \times (-7 + 5)))$$

$$47576 := (F(4!) + ((7 + F((5 + 7))) \times F(6)))$$

$$47578 := (F(4!) + (F(7) - (-57) \times F(8)))$$

$$47580 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 0$$

$$47581 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 1$$

$$47582 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 2$$

$$47583 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 3$$

$$47584 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 4$$

$$47585 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 5$$

$$47586 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 6$$

$$47587 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 7$$

$$47588 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 8$$

$$47589 := F(4)! \times F(7) \times F(5!/8) + 9$$

$$47592 := (F(4!) + (((F(7) + 5) \times F(9)) \times 2))$$

$$47593 := (F(4!) + ((7 \times 5)^{F(9/3)}))$$

$$47594 := ((F(4!) - F(7)) + (59 \times F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$47596 := ((F(F(4)) \times (-((F(7) - 5!) \times F(9)))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$47599 := (F(4!) + (((F(7) + 5!) \times 9) + F(9)))$$

$$47604 := -(((F(F((F(4))!)) - (F(7) \times F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))) + (F((F(4))!))!))$$

$$47612 := -(((F((F(4))!))! + (-F(7)) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 1)) - F(2))))$$

$$47616 := (F(4!) - (F(7) \times (-6 \times 16)))$$

$$47622 := (((-4!) + F(F(7))) \times 6) + F(((2 + 2))!))$$

$$47623 := (-F(F(4))) + ((F(7) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) - (F(3))!))$$

$$47624 := (F(4!) + ((7! / (6 - 2)) - (4)))$$

$$47625 := ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + ((6 - 2)^5))$$

$$47626 := (F(4!) + ((7! - F(6)) / (-2 - 6)))$$

$$47628 := (F(4!) + (7! / ((6 \times 2) - 8)))$$

$$47629 := (F(4!) + (F(7) \times (F(6) + F((2 + 9)))))$$

$$47630 := (F(4!) + ((7! + F(6)) / (3 + 0!)))$$

$$47632 := (F(4!) + (((7! / F(6)) + F(3)) \times 2))$$

$$47633 := ((4! + F(F(7))) + ((6! + (3!^{3!})))$$

$$47634 := (F(4!) + ((7! + (F(6) \times 3)) / 4))$$

$$47635 := (F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times 3!) - (5)))$$

$$47636 := (F(4!) + (((7! / F(6)) \times F(3)) + F(6)))$$

$$47638 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times (-3 - 8)))$$

$$47640 := F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4)! + 0$$

$$47641 := F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4)! + 1$$

$$47642 := F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4)! + 2$$

$$47643 := F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4)! + 3$$

$$47644 := F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4)! + 4$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47645 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 5 \\
 47646 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 6 \\
 47647 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 7 \\
 47648 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 8 \\
 47649 &:= F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) + F(4!) + 9 \\
 \\
 47651 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(7) - (6^{5-1}))) \\
 47652 &:= ((-4!) + F(F(7))) \times ((6 - 5!) \times (-2)) \\
 47653 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(7))! / (F(6))!) / 5!) - F(3)) \\
 47654 &:= (((F(4))! \times F(F(7))) + (F(6) - 5!)) + F(4!) \\
 47655 &:= (F(4!) + ((-(F(7))! / (F((6!/5!)))! / (-5!))) \\
 47656 &:= ((((-4) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(6))) - 5!) + (F(6))! \\
 47662 &:= (((F(4)! / 7) + (F(6))!) + ((6! - 2))) \\
 47663 &:= (((F(4)! / 7) + (F(6))!) + (6!)) - F(F(3)) \\
 47666 &:= (((((F(4))!)! - (7!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (-6!) - (F(6))!) \\
 47668 &:= (((F(4))! + (F(7) - 6!)) \times (-68)) \\
 47670 &:= (((F(4) \times F(7)) - 6!) \times (-70)) \\
 47673 &:= (((F(4)! / (-7)) + F(6)) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 47674 &:= (4 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (7! / 4!))) \\
 47674 &:= (4 + ((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (7! / 4!))) \\
 47675 &:= (((F(4))! + (((F(7) + 6!) \times F(7)))) \times 5) \\
 47676 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - (F(6) + (7))) \times 6)) \\
 47678 &:= (F(4!) + (((-F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7))) / 8)) \\
 47679 &:= ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times 7) - ((-6) \times F(F(7))) \times F(9)) \\
 47683 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - 83)) \\
 47684 &:= ((F(4!) - 7) + (F(F(6)) \times (F(8) \times F(4)))) \\
 47685 &:= ((-F(4) \times F(F(7))) - ((-6) \times 8!) / 5) \\
 47686 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times (F(8) + F(6)))) \\
 47688 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 + F(6)) \times 88)) \\
 47690 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times F(F(6))) \times 9) - 0!)) \\
 47691 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 \times F(F(6))) \times (9 \times 1))) \\
 47692 &:= (F(4!) + (((-F(7)) \times F(F(6))) + F((F(9) / 2)))) \\
 47693 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times F(F(6))) \times 9) + F(3))) \\
 47694 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 + 6) \times F(9)) \times F(4))) \\
 47695 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) - ((F(F(6)) - F(9)) \times 5!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47696 &:= (((F(4))!)! + (((-7!) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(9)) \times F(6))) \\
 47697 &:= (((F(4))! \times F((7 + F(6)))) + 9) \times F(7) \\
 47698 &:= ((F(4!)/7) + ((6! + F(9)) + 8!)) \\
 47716 &:= -((((F((F(4))!))! + (F(7) \times (-7) - F((-1 + F(F(6))))))))) \\
 47718 &:= (((F(4))! \times 7!) - F(F(7))) + F((1 + F(8))) \\
 47720 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7) \times F(7)) \times F((2 + 0!)!))) \\
 47724 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - 7) \times (2 + 4))) \\
 47728 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(7) \times F(7)) + F(2)) \times 8)) \\
 47731 &:= (((F(4))! - 7!) \times (-F(7))) - F((F(F(3!)) + 1)) \\
 47732 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) + F((F(7) + F(3)) + 2)) \\
 47733 &:= (((-((4^7)) + F(F(7))) \times (-3)) - 3!!) \\
 47734 &:= (((F((4! - 7))) - F(F(7))) + F(3)) + F(4!)) \\
 47736 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(7) \times F(7)) + F(3)) \times F(6))) \\
 47737 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) - 7) \times 3!) + F(7))) \\
 47738 &:= ((F(4!) - 7) + ((F(F(7)) \times 3!) - (F(8)))) \\
 47739 &:= ((F(4!) + 7) + ((F(F(7)) \times 3!) - F(9))) \\
 47743 &:= ((F(4!) + F(7)) + ((F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) \times 3!)) \\
 47744 &:= ((F(4!) + 7) + ((F(7) + 4!)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 47746 &:= (((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) - F(F(7))) \times (F(4))! - F(6)) \\
 47747 &:= (F(4!) + (7 \times ((7!/4!) - F(7))) \\
 47748 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times F(F(7))) - 7) \times 4) + 8! \\
 47749 &:= -((F(F((F(4))!)) - ((7 + (F(F(7)) \times (F(4))!)) \times F(9))) \\
 47753 &:= (F(4!) - (((F(7) \times (F(7) - 5!)) + 3!)) \\
 47754 &:= (((F(4))! \times F(F(7))) - (7 + 5)) + F(4!) \\
 47755 &:= (((F(F((F(4))!)) + (F((7 + 7)))) \times 5!) - (5)) \\
 47758 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + ((F(F(7)) \times 5) - 8)) \\
 47759 &:= (((F(4))! \times F(F(7))) - 7) + F((-((5 - 9))!)) \\
 47760 &:= ((F(4!) - 7) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-6)) - 0!)) \\
 47761 &:= (F(4!) + (7 \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(6) + 1)))) \\
 47762 &:= -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((F(F(7)) - (7^6))/(-2))) \\
 47763 &:= (F((-((F(4) - 7))))!) + ((F(F(7)) \times 6) - 3) \\
 47764 &:= (((4 \times F(7)) \times F(7)) + 6!) + F(4!) \\
 47765 &:= ((4! + (F(7) \times (F(7) + 6!))) \times 5) \\
 47766 &:= (F(4!) + (F(F(7)) \times ((7 - 6) \times 6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}47768 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(7) \times F(7)) + (6)) \times 8)) \\47772 &:= (F(4!) + ((-7) + F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(2))) \\47773 &:= (((F(4)!) \times F(F(7))) + 7) + F(((7 - 3)!)) \\47774 &:= (((F(4)!) \times F(F(7))) + F((-7) + F(7))) + F(4!) \\47774 &:= (((F(4)!) \times F(F(7))) + F((-7) + F(7))) + F(4!) \\47776 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(7) \times F(7)) + (7)) \times F(6))) \\47779 &:= (((F(4)!) \times F(F(7))) + F(7)) + F(((F(7) - 9)!)) \\47782 &:= ((F((F(4)!))!) + (F(7) \times (7 \times 82))) \\47783 &:= (((F(F(4)) - (7!)) \times (-F(7))) - F((F(8) + F(F(3)))))) \\47785 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) \times ((F(7) \times 8) + (5)))) \\47787 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times F(F(7))) + (F(8))) - F(F(7)))) \\47789 &:= (F(4!) + (7 \times (F(F(7)) - (F(8) + 9)))) \\47790 &:= (F(4) \times (-7!) + (F(F(7)) \times 90)) \\47793 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) + 9) \times 3)) \\47794 &:= (((((F(4)!) \times F(F(7))) + 7) \times F(9)) + (4!)) \\47795 &:= (((F(4)!) + (F(F(7)) \times (7 + F(9)))) \times 5) \\47796 &:= ((4 \times 7) \times (F((7 + 9)) + 6!)) \\47798 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7) + F(7)) \times (F(9) + F(8)))) \\47799 &:= (((4 + F(F(7))) + ((7! + F(9)))) \times 9) \\47804 &:= (((F(4)!)! - (-7!) + F((F(8) + 0!))) \times (-4)) \\47814 &:= (((F(4)!) \times ((7!/F(8)) + 1)) + F(4!)) \\47815 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) - (-8!)/(-(1 - 5)!)) \\47818 &:= (((F(4)!)! + ((F(7) + 8!) + F((-1 + F(8)))))) \\47822 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 + ((8 - 2)!) \times 2)) \\47823 &:= (((F(4)!) - (7!)) \times (F(8) - 2))/(-F(3)) \\47824 &:= (F(4!) + (-((7 \times 8)) \times (-2 - 4!)) \\47826 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) + (8 + 2)) \times 6)) \\47828 &:= (((F((F(4)!))!) - (-F(7) + F(F(8)))) \times 2) - F(F(8)) \\47832 &:= (F(4) \times ((7! + F(F(8))) - (F(F(3)) \times 2)) \\47833 &:= (((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (8^3)) + 3!)) \\47834 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7) + ((8 - F(3))!) \times F(F(4)))) \\47835 &:= (-F(4) + (((7! + F(F(8))) \times 3) - 5!)) \\47836 &:= (F(4!) + ((7 + F(8)) + (F(3) \times 6!)) \\47837 &:= (F(4!) + ((-7) + ((8 - 3)!) \times F(7)) \\47838 &:= (F(4!) + ((7! - 8!)/(-(3 \times 8)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47842 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) + ((F(8) \times 4!))) \times 2)) \\ 47843 &:= (((F(4)^7) + 8) + F(4!)) - 3!! \\ 47844 &:= (((F(4))! - ((7! - 8!)/4!)) + F(4!)) \\ 47846 &:= (F(4!) - (((7! - 8!)/4! - F(6)))) \\ 47847 &:= (F(4) \times ((7! + F(F(8))) - (4! + F(7)))) \\ 47848 &:= (F(4!) + ((-7) + (8 \times 4!)) \times 8) \\ 47849 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) + (((8!/4!) + F(9)))) \\ 47852 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - (F(8))) \times (5 + 2))) \\ 47853 &:= ((F(4) \times (7! + F(F(8)))) - (5 \times F(F(3)))) \\ 47854 &:= -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (((-7) \times 8!) \times (-5)/4!)) \\ 47856 &:= (-(((4! - 7!) - (F(8) \times 5!))) + (F(6))!) \\ 47857 &:= (F(F(F((F(4))!))) + ((7! + F((8 + 5))) \times 7)) \\ 47858 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (-7!) + F(F(8))) + F((5!/8))) \\ 47859 &:= (((F(4))! - F((-7) + F(8))) \times (-5! + 9)) \\ 47860 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (F((-7) + F(8))) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)) \\ 47863 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) + ((F(8) + 6!) \times F(3)))) \\ 47864 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times ((7 + F(8)) + 6!)) + F(4!)) \\ 47865 &:= ((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) + (8! + (6^5))) \\ 47867 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (((7! + 8!)/6) - F(7))) \\ 47868 &:= ((F(4) \times (7! + F(F(8)))) - (6!/8)) \\ 47873 &:= ((F(4!) + F(F(7))) - ((-F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (-3!))) \\ 47874 &:= ((4 + F(F(7))) \times (-8) + (7!/4!)) \\ 47874 &:= ((4 + F(F(7))) \times (-8) + (7!/4!)) \\ 47875 &:= (-4) + (F((-7) + F(8))) \times (7 + 5!)) \\ 47878 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (-7!) + F(F(8))) + (7!/8)) \\ 47879 &:= ((F(4) \times (7! + F(F(8)))) - 79) \\ 47883 &:= ((((-4) + 7!) - F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 3) \\ 47884 &:= (((4 \times F((-7) + F(8))) + 8) + F(4!)) \\ 47885 &:= (((F(4))! + (-7) \times F(F(8)))/(-8)) \times 5) \\ 47887 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - (8 + 8)) \times 7)) \\ 47889 &:= (F(4!) + (F(7) \times ((-8) + F(8)) \times 9)) \\ 47892 &:= ((-4) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(8)))) + ((9 - 2)!) \\ 47893 &:= ((F(4!) + F(7)) + ((F(8) \times 9) \times F(3!))) \\ 47895 &:= ((F(F((F(4))!)) - (7! + F(F(8)))) \times (-F((9 - 5)))) \\ 47896 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - (8 + F(9))) \times F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47897 &:= ((F((4! - (7))) \times (F(8) + 9)) - F(7)) \\
 47904 &:= (F(4!) + (((7 \times 9) + 0!) \times 4!)) \\
 47913 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (7! + ((F(9) + 1)^3))) \\
 47914 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (7! + ((F(9) + 1)^{F(4)}))) \\
 47919 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7) + F(9)) \times (-1 + F(9)))) \\
 47923 &:= (F((F(4))!) + (7! + ((F(9) + F(2))^3))) \\
 47928 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(7))! / (9! + ((2 + 8)!))) \\
 47930 &:= ((F(4) \times ((7! - 9) + F(F(F(3!)))))) - 0! \\
 47931 &:= ((F((4! - (7))) - F(9)) + F(((3 + 1)!)) \\
 47932 &:= ((F(4) \times ((7! - 9) + F(F(F(3!)))))) + F(2) \\
 47933 &:= (F(F(4)) + (((7! - 9) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 3)) \\
 47934 &:= ((F((4! - (7))) - (F(9) - 3)) + F(4!)) \\
 47935 &:= ((F(4!) - F(F(7))) - ((-9) - 3!) \times 5!) \\
 47936 &:= (F(4!) + (7 \times ((F(9) - 3!) \times F(6)))) \\
 47937 &:= (F(4) \times ((-7) + F(F(F((9 - 3)))))) + (7!)) \\
 47938 &:= -((((F(4))! - (7! \times 9)) - F((-3) + F(8)))) \\
 \\
 47940 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 0 \\
 47941 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 1 \\
 47942 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 2 \\
 47943 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 3 \\
 47944 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 4 \\
 47945 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 5 \\
 47946 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 6 \\
 47947 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 7 \\
 47948 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 8 \\
 47949 &:= (F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9) \times F(4)! + 9 \\
 \\
 47951 &:= (((F(4))! \times 7!) + F((F(F((F((9 - 5))))!)) + 1))) \\
 47952 &:= ((F(4!) - F(7)) + F((F(9) / F((5 - 2)))) \\
 47953 &:= -((F((F(4))!) - ((F(F(7)) - (9 + 5))^{F(3)})) \\
 47954 &:= (((F((F(4))!) + (F(F(7)) \times F(9))) / 5) + F(4!)) \\
 47955 &:= (F(4!) + (F((7 + 9)) - (5! \times (-5)))) \\
 47956 &:= ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-7)) - (-((9^5) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 47957 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) - (F((9 - 5)))!) \times 7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$47958 := ((F(4!) - 7) + F((-((9 - 5)) + F(8))))$$

$$47960 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 0$$

$$47961 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 1$$

$$47962 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 2$$

$$47963 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 3$$

$$47964 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 4$$

$$47965 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 5$$

$$47966 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 6$$

$$47967 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 7$$

$$47968 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 8$$

$$47969 := F(4!) + (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(6) + 9$$

$$47970 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(7)) + F(9)) \times (7 - 0!)))$$

$$47972 := ((F(4!) + 7) + F(((9 + 7) + F(2))))$$

$$47973 := ((F(4!) + F(((F(7) - 9) + F(7)))) + F(3!))$$

$$47974 := ((F((4! - (7))) + 9) + F(((7 - F(4))!))$$

$$47974 := ((F((4! - (7))) + 9) + F(((7 - F(4))!))$$

$$47975 := (F(4!) + ((F(7) + F(9)) + (F(7) \times 5!)))$$

$$47976 := (F(4) \times ((7! + F((F(9) - F(7)))) + 6))$$

$$47977 := ((F(4!) - (F(7) + 9)) + (7 \times F(F(7))))$$

$$47978 := (F(4!) + (-7) \times ((F(9) \times (-7)) + 8))$$

$$47979 := (F(4!) + (F(7) + ((F(9) + F(7)) \times F(9))))$$

$$47982 := (F(4) \times (((7! + 9) + F(F(8))) - F(2)))$$

$$47983 := ((F(4) \times ((7! + 9) + F(F(8)))) - F(3))$$

$$47984 := (((4! \times 7) + F(9)) \times 8) + F(4!)$$

$$47986 := (F(4!) + ((F(7) + F((9 + 8))) + F(6)))$$

$$47989 := ((F(4!) + ((F(7) - 9))!) + (F((8 + 9))))$$

$$47992 := ((F(4!) + (-7) + F(9)) + F((F(9)/2)))$$

$$47994 := (((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(9)) + 9) \times (F(4)!)$$

$$47998 := ((4! \times (7! - F((9 + 9)))) - F(F(8)))$$

$$47999 := ((F(4!) + F((F((F((F(7) - 9))!) + 9))) + F(9))$$

$$48000 := ((F(4))! \times 8000)$$

$$48009 := ((F((F(4))!))! - (F(F((8 - 0!))) \times (0! - F(9))))$$

$$48025 := (((F((F(4))!))! / F(8)) + 0!) \times 25$$

- 48027 := (F(F((F(4)!)) × (((8 - 0!)/2) - F(F(7))))
- 48036 := ((F(4)! × ((F(8) - 0!)³) + (6))
- 48039 := (F(4!) + ((8!/(0! + 3))! - 9))
- 48043 := (((-4) + 8!) - 0!) + (F(4!)/3!))
- 48044 := (F(4!) + ((8!/(04)!) - (4)))
- 48045 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((F(8) - 0!)) - (F((F(4)! × (-5!))))
- 48046 := (-(((F(4) - 8!) - 0!)) + (F(4!)/6))
- 48047 := (((F(4)!)! + ((F((F(8) - 0!)) - 4) × 7))
- 48048 := (F(4!) + (8!/(((0 - 4) + 8)!))
- 48053 := ((F(4!) + F(F(8))) - (F(F((0! + (5))))³))
- 48054 := (F(4!) + ((8!/(-(0! - (5))))! + (F(4)!))
- 48056 := (F(4!) + ((8 × (0! + 5!)) + 6!))
- 48064 := (F(4!) + ((-F(8) + F(F((0! + (6)))) × F((F(4)!)))
- 48067 := (((F(4)!)! - 8) + (F((-0! + F(F(6)))) × 7))
- 48069 := (F(4!) + (F(8) × ((0! + F(6)) × 9))
- 48073 := -(F(F(4)) + ((F((F(8) - 0!)) × (-7)) - 3!))
- 48074 := (((F(4)!)! + (F((F(8) - 0!)) × 7)) - F(F(F(4))))
- 48075 := ((F(4) × (F(F(8)) - ((0! - 7!)))) + 5!)
- 48076 := ((F(F(4)) × F((8 + 0!))) × -(F(7) - 6!))
- 48084 := (F(4!) + ((F((8 - 0!))!/(8 + F(F(4))))!))
- 48084 := (F(4!) + ((F((8 - 0!))!/(8 + F(F(4))))!))
- 48085 := ((F(4!) + F(((8 + 0!) + 8))) + 5!)
- 48093 := ((F(4!) + F((F(8) - 0!)) - ((9 - F(3)))!)
- 48094 := (((F(4)⁸) - 0!) × 9) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))
- 48095 := (((F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8))) × (-0!)) + (9⁵))
- 48103 := (((4!/8)¹⁰) - F(F(F(3))))
- 48114 := ((F(4)⁸⁻¹) × (1 + F(F((F(4)!))))
- 48132 := (F(4!) + ((F(8) × F((1 × 3)))²))
- 48144 := ((F(4)! × (((F(8) - 1)^{F(4)}) + 4!))
- 48148 := (F(4!) + ((F(8) - 1) × F((F(4) + 8))))
- 48165 := (((F(4)!)! + (F(8))) × (1 × 65))
- 48168 := (F(4!) + (((F(8) - 1) × 6!)/8))
- 48174 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(8) × (F((1 + F(7))) - F(4))))
- 48176 := (F(4!) + ((F(F((8 - 1))) - 7) × F(6)))
- 48177 := ((F(4!) - (F(8) - F(17))) + F(F(7)))

$$48184 := (((F(4))! - F(F((8 - 1)))) \times (-8)) + F(4!))$$

$$48184 := (((F(4))! - F(F((8 - 1)))) \times (-8)) + F(4!))$$

$$48194 := (F(4!) + ((F(F(8)) + (1 + 9)) / (F(4)!)))$$

$$48195 := (F(4!) + (F(8) \times ((1 - F(9)) + 5!)))$$

$$48198 := ((F(4!) + F(F((8 - 1)))) + (F((9 + 8))))$$

$$48208 := ((F((F(4))!) \times (F((8 \times 2)) - 0!)) + 8!)$$

$$48216 := ((F(4!) - ((8! + (21)))) \times F(6))$$

$$48224 := (F(4!) + ((F(F((8 - F(2)))) - F(2)) \times F((F(4))!)))$$

$$48225 := -(((F((F(4))!))! - ((F((F(8) + F(2))) - 2) \times 5)))$$

$$48231 := (F(4!) + ((8 \times F(F((F(2) + 3!)))) - 1))$$

$$48232 := (F(4!) + (8 \times F(F(((2 + 3) + 2))))))$$

$$48233 := (((F((F(4) + 8))^2) - F(3!)) + (F(3!)!))$$

$$48234 := (((F(4) + (8^2)) \times (3!)!) - (F(4))!)$$

$$48235 := (((F(4) + (8^2)) \times (3!)!) - (5))$$

$$48237 := (F(4!) + (F(8) \times F((F(2) + (3 + 7))))))$$

$$48238 := ((F((F(4) + 8))^2) - (3 - 8!))$$

$$48239 := (-((F(4) - 8!)) - (F(F((F(2) + 3!)))) \times (-F(9))))$$

$$48240 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 0$$

$$48241 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 1$$

$$48242 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 2$$

$$48243 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 3$$

$$48244 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 4$$

$$48245 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 5$$

$$48246 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 6$$

$$48247 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 7$$

$$48248 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 8$$

$$48249 := F(4)!! \times (8^2 + F(4)) + 9$$

$$48253 := (F((-4) + F(8))) + (((F(2) + (5))^{3!})))$$

$$48256 := (F(((4 + 8) + 2)) \times (5! + F(6)))$$

$$48258 := (F(4!) + ((F(8) \times ((2 \times 5)!)) / 8!))$$

$$48259 := (F(4!) + (F(8) + (F((2 \times 5)) \times F(9))))$$

$$48264 := (((F(4) + (8^2)) \times 6!) + 4!)$$

$$48265 := -(((F((F(4))!))! + ((F((F(8) + F(2))) + 6) \times (-5))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48266 &:= ((F(4!) - (F(8) + F(2))) + ((F(6)!/F(F(6)))) \\ 48268 &:= ((F(4!) - (F(8) - F(2))) + ((F(6)!/F(8))) \\ 48274 &:= (F(4!) + (((8 - 2)! + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)))) \\ 48276 &:= (F(4!) + ((8 + F(2)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(6)))) \\ 48277 &:= -(((F(F(4)) - (8! + (2^{F(7)}))) + F(F(7)))) \\ 48279 &:= (F(4!) + ((8!/F((F(2) + (7)))) - 9)) \\ 48283 &:= (((4!)/(F(8)!)) - F((-2) + F(8))) + (F(3!))! \\ 48284 &:= (F(4!) + (((8! \times F(2))/F(8)) - (4))) \\ 48284 &:= (F(4!) + (((8! \times F(2))/F(8)) - (4))) \\ 48286 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(8) \times (-2)) + 8!)/F(F(6)))) \\ 48287 &:= ((F(4!) + F((8 + 2))) - (-8 \times F(F(7)))) \\ 48288 &:= (F((48/2)) + (8!/F(8))) \\ 48293 &:= (F(4!) + (F((8 + 2)) \times (F(9) + F(F(3)))) \\ 48294 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) \times 9)))/F(4)) \\ 48295 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (((F(8)!/(2 \times 9)!)) - (5))) \\ 48296 &:= ((F(4!) - ((8! + (2 + 9)))) \times F(6)) \\ 48297 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (F((8 + 2)) - (-F(9)) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 48298 &:= -((F(F(4)) - (((F(8)!/(2 \times 9)!)) + 8!)) \\ 48305 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (F(((8 \times F(3)) + 0!)) \times 5)) \\ 48308 &:= (F(4!) + ((8!/F(F(3!))) - ((0! - F(8)))) \\ 48309 &:= (F(4!) - ((-8!/F(F(3!))) - F(-((0! - 9)))) \\ 48313 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((F(F(8)) + ((3! + 1)!)/F(3))) \\ 48314 &:= (-(((F(4)! - 8!)) + ((F(F(3!)) - 1)^{F(4)})) \\ 48320 &:= (((F(4!) - 8!) - F(3!)) \times F(((2 + 0!)!)) \\ 48323 &:= ((F(4) + 8!) + ((F(F(3!)) - F(2))^3)) \\ 48324 &:= ((4 + 8!) + ((F(F(3!)) - F(2))^{F(4)})) \\ 48326 &:= (F(4!) + (F((8 + 3)) \times (F(2) + F(F(6)))) \\ 48327 &:= (F(4) \times (((F(8) \times 3!)^2) + F(F(7)))) \\ 48328 &:= ((F(4!) - (((8! + 3!) + F(2)))) \times 8) \\ 48329 &:= (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - F((F(2) + 9))) \\ 48333 &:= (((F(4!) - ((8! + 3!))) \times F(3!)) - 3) \\ 48334 &:= (((-4) + F((8 \times F(3)))) \times F(3)) + F(4!) \\ 48336 &:= ((F(4)! \times ((8!/(F(3) + 3)) - F(6))) \\ 48337 &:= ((4 \times F(F(8))) - (((3!)! \times (-3!)) - F(F(7)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$48338 := (((F(4!)/(-F(8))) + (F(3!)!) - (((3!)! - F(F(8))))))$$

$$48339 := (F(4!) + ((-F(8)) + ((3!)!/3) \times 9))$$

$$48340 := (((F(4)^8) \times 3) + F((4! - 0!)))$$

$$48341 := (((F(F(4)) \times F((8 \times F(3)))) + F(4!)) - 1)$$

$$48342 := (F(4!) + ((8 - 3!) \times F((4^2))))$$

$$48343 := (((F(F(4)) \times F((8 \times F(3)))) + F(4!)) + F(F(3)))$$

$$48344 := (((F(F(4)) \times F((8 \times F(3)))) + F(4!)) + F(F(4)))$$

$$48345 := (F(4!) + (((-F(8)) + 3!!) \times F(4) - 5!))$$

$$48346 := (4 + ((-F(F(8))) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(4!) \times 6))$$

$$48347 := (F(4!) + ((83 \times 4!) - F(7)))$$

$$48348 := (F(4!) + (((-((8 + 3)!) \times F(F(4)))/(-8!)))$$

$$48349 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(9))$$

$$48352 := (F(4!) + ((F((8 \times F(3))) + (5)) \times 2))$$

$$48354 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - (5!/4))$$

$$48356 := (-4) + (-8) \times ((3!)! - F((5!/6)))$$

$$48358 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - (5 + F(8)))$$

$$48360 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 0$$

$$48361 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 1$$

$$48362 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 2$$

$$48363 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 3$$

$$48364 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 4$$

$$48365 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 5$$

$$48366 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 6$$

$$48367 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 7$$

$$48368 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 8$$

$$48369 := (F(4!) - 8! - 3) \times F(6) + 9$$

$$48370 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - (F(7) + 0!))$$

$$48371 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - F((7 \times 1)))$$

$$48372 := ((F(4)!) \times (-((8!/(F(3) - (7))) + 2)))$$

$$48373 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - (F(7) - F(3)))$$

$$48374 := (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - (F(7) - F(4)))$$

$$48376 := ((-4) \times F(F(8))) + ((F(3)^7) \times 6!))$$

$$48377 := (((F(4!) + 8!)/F(3)) + (7! - (7)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48378 &:= -(((F(4))! + ((8!/(F(3) - (7))) - 8!))) \\ 48379 &:= (((4^8) + 3) + ((F(7))!/(-9!))) \\ 48381 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) + (-8) \times ((3!)! - F((F(8) - 1)))) \\ 48383 &:= (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - F((8 - 3!))) \\ 48385 &:= (((F(4) + 8!) - F(3)) + (8!/5)) \\ 48386 &:= (F(F(4)) - ((8! - F((3 \times 8))) \times F(6))) \\ 48387 &:= (F(4) + ((8! \times 3!)/(-8) + F(7))) \\ 48388 &:= (4 + ((8! - F((3 \times 8))) \times (-8))) \\ 48392 &:= (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) + (9 - F(2))) \\ 48393 &:= (F(4!) + (((8 - 3) \times 9)^{F(3)})) \\ 48394 &:= (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) + (F(9) - 4!)) \\ 48395 &:= (((((F(4))! \times (-8!)) - F((F(F(3)) + 9)))/(-5)) \\ 48396 &:= (((((4!)!/(F(8))!) \times (-F(3))) - 9!)/(-F(6))) \\ 48397 &:= (((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(-(3 - 9))) + F(7)) \\ 48398 &:= (((F(4))! \times F(F(8))) + ((F(3) - (9!/F(8)))) \\ 48400 &:= (F((F(4))!) \times ((-8!) + F(4!)) + (0! + 0!)) \\ 48404 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) - 0!) + F(F((F(4))!))) \\ 48405 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(8) \times ((4! - 0!) - 5!))) \\ 48406 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) + (0! + F(F(6)))) \\ 48408 &:= (4! - ((8! \times 4!)/(0! - F(8))) \\ 48413 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times ((-8!) + F(4!)) + 1)) + F(F(3!)) \\ 48416 &:= (F(4!) - (-8) \times (F((4 - 1)^{F(6)})) \\ 48418 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) + F((1 + 8))) \\ 48419 &:= ((F((F(4))!) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) + (1 + F(9))) \\ 48420 &:= ((-((4! \times 8!)) - ((F(4))!)!)/(-20)) \\ 48424 &:= (F(4!) + (((8^{F(4)}) + 2) \times 4)) \\ 48425 &:= (F(4!) + ((F(8) - (4)) \times (F(2) + 5!))) \\ 48429 &:= -((((F(4))!)! - (((F(F(8)) - (4!))/2) \times 9)) \\ 48431 &:= (((((F(4))! - 8!) + F(4!)) \times F(3!)) - 1) \\ 48432 &:= (((((4!)!/(F(8))!) \times 4) - F((3! \times 2))) \\ 48433 &:= (((((F(4))! - 8!) + F(4!)) \times F(3!)) + F(F(3))) \\ 48434 &:= (((((F(4))! - 8!) + F(4!)) \times F(3!)) + F(F(4))) \\ 48435 &:= (((((4!)!/(F(8))!) \times 4) - F(F(3!))) - 5!) \\ 48436 &:= (4 + (((8! - F(4!)) - 3!) \times (-F(6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48437 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(8))) + (F(F(4))^{-F(3)+F(7)})) \\
 48438 &:= (F(4!) + (((F(8) + F(F(4))) \times (3!))/8)) \\
 48439 &:= ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) + F((F(F(3)) + 9))) \\
 48440 &:= (F((F(4)!)) \times (((-8!) + (F(4)!)) + F(4!)) + 0!) \\
 48444 &:= (F((4 + 8)) - ((F(4!)/(-4!)) - F(4!))) \\
 48445 &:= ((F(4!) + F((F(8) - (4)))) - (-4 \times 5!)) \\
 48446 &:= (-F(F(4))) - (((-8!) + F((F(4)!)) + F(4!)) \times (-F(6))) \\
 48447 &:= ((-((F(4) \times (F(8)^4))) - F(4!))/(-F(7))) \\
 48448 &:= ((F(4!) + F((F(8) - F(4)))) - ((4! \times F(8)))) \\
 48449 &:= (((F(4)^8) + F(4!)) + ((F((F(4)!))!)/(-9))) \\
 48453 &:= (((4!)/(F(8)!)) \times 4) - ((5! + 3)) \\
 48454 &:= (((F(4!)/F(8)) - F(F(4))) - 5!) + F(4!) \\
 48456 &:= ((F(4!) - ((8! - (4 + 5)))) \times F(6)) \\
 48457 &:= ((F(4!) - 8) + ((4 + 5) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 48458 &:= (-F(4!)) + (((-F(8)) + ((F(4)!))! \times 5!) + F(F(8))) \\
 48459 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + (-F(8)) - (F(F(4)) \times (-5! \times F(9)))) \\
 48463 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(8) - (46^{F(3)}))) \\
 48464 &:= (F(4!) + (8 - ((4! - 6!) \times F(4)))) \\
 48465 &:= (F(4!) + ((8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times F((F(6) + (5)))) \\
 48467 &:= (F(4) + (-(((8^{F(4)}) - 6!) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 48468 &:= ((4 \times F(8)) - ((F(4!) - (F(6)!)) \times (-8))) \\
 48469 &:= ((F(4!) + ((F(8) \times 4!)) + F((F(6) + 9))) \\
 48472 &:= (F((F(4)!)) \times ((-8!) + F(4!)) + (F(7) - 2)) \\
 48473 &:= ((F(4!) + 8) + ((F(4) \times F(F(7))) \times 3)) \\
 48474 &:= (((((F(4)! + (F(8))) \times (F(4)!)) \times F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 48475 &:= ((F((F(4)!))! + ((-((F(8)/F(4))) \times F(F(7))) \times (-5))) \\
 48476 &:= (((4! \times F(F(8))) + (F(4)!)/7) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 48478 &:= (((F(4)^8) + F((4! - (7)))) + 8!) \\
 48479 &:= (-((4! - 8!)) + ((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) - 9)) \\
 48480 &:= ((-4) + F((F(8) - (F(4)!))) \times 80) \\
 48483 &:= (F(4!) - ((F(8) - (4! \times F((8 + 3)))))) \\
 48484 &:= (((((4!)/(F(8)!)) - F(F(4))) - (F(8))) \times 4) \\
 48484 &:= (((((4!)/(F(8)!)) - F(F(4))) - (F(8))) \times 4) \\
 48486 &:= (F(4!) + (F(8) - (F(4) \times (F(8) - 6!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 48487 := $-\left(\left(F(F(F(4))) - (8 \times (F(4!) - ((8! - F(7))))\right)\right)$
- 48489 := $(F(4!) - ((F(8) - ((F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(9))))$
- 48492 := $(4 \times (-F(8)) + ((4!)! / (F((9 - F(2))))!))$
- 48493 := $((F(4!) / (-8)) + ((F((4 + 9))^{F(3)}))$
- 48494 := $((F(4) \times ((F((8 - 4))!)!) + (-F(9)) + F(4!))$
- 48495 := $((F((F(4))!) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) - (9 - 5!))$
- 48496 := $(F(4!) - ((8! \times (-4) - F(9)) / 6!))$
- 48497 := $(F(4!) + (((F(8) \times F(4)) \times F(9)) - F(7)))$
- 48499 := $(F(4!) + ((F(F((F(8) / F(4)))) \times 9) + F(9)))$
- 48504 := $((F(4))! \times (8! / 5) + ((0! + (4)))!)$
- 48505 := $((F(4))! \times (8! / 5) + ((0! + 5!))$
- 48510 := $(F(F((F(4))!)) \times (F(8) \times (5! - 10)))$
- 48512 := $((F(F(4))^{8+5}) + (F(((1 + 2))!)!))$
- 48513 := $((F(F(4))^{8+5}) + 1) + (F(3!)!)$
- 48516 := $((F(4))! \times (((8! / 5) + 1) + F(F(6))))$
- 48524 := $((F(4!) / F(8)) - 52) + F(4!)$
- 48526 := $-\left(\left(F(4!) + F(F(8))\right) - \left(\left(5 + 2\right)! \times F(F(6))\right)\right)$
- 48531 := $(F(4!) + ((8 - 5) \times ((3!)! + 1)))$
- 48533 := $((F((F(4) \times 8)) + (5)) + (3 \times (3!)!))$
- 48534 := $(-\left(\left(\left(F(4) - F(8)\right) \times 5!\right) - 3!\right) + F(4!))$
- 48536 := $((4! + (8! / 5)) \times 3!) + F(6)$
- 48539 := $(F(4!) + (((F(8) \times 5) \times F(F(3!))) - F(9)))$
- 48543 := $(F((F(4) \times 8)) + ((5 + ((F(4))!)!) \times 3))$
- 48544 := $(((((4!)! / (F(8))!) - (5 + F(4))) \times 4)$
- 48546 := $((4! - ((8! / (-5)) - F(4))) \times 6)$
- 48547 := $((F(4!) - F(((8 - 5))!)) + ((F(4)^7)))$
- 48548 := $(((((F(4))! - F(F(8))) / (-5)) + F(4!)) - 8)$
- 48549 := $(((((4 + F(F(8))) / 5) + F(4!)) - 9)$
- 48553 := $((F(F((F(4))!)) - F(F(8))) / (-5)) + F(((5 - F(F(3))))!))$
- 48554 := $((F((F(4))!) - F((F(8) + (5)))) / (-5)) \times F(F(4))$
- 48562 := $((4! + F(F(8))) / 5) + F(((6 - 2))!)$
- 48565 := $(F(4!) + ((8 + 5)^{F(6)-5}))$
- 48567 := $(F(4!) + ((8 - 5) \times (6! + F(7))))$
- 48573 := $(F(4!) + (F(8) \times ((5 \times 7) \times 3)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 48574 &:= (((F(4!)/F(8)) + ((5 - 7))) + F(4!)) \\ 48576 &:= (((4!)/(F(8)!)) \times ((5 - 7) + 6)) \\ 48577 &:= ((4 \times (F(F(8)) - 5!)) + (F(F(7)) + (7!))) \\ 48578 &:= ((4! \times (8 + (5! \times F(7)))) + F(F(8))) \\ 48584 &:= (((((4!)/(F(8)!)) + F(-(5 - 8)))) \times 4) \\ 48584 &:= (((((4!)/(F(8)!)) + F(-(5 - 8)))) \times 4) \\ 48587 &:= ((((((F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 5!) - ((8! + F(7)))))) \\ 48594 &:= (((F(4)! \times ((8!/5) + F(9))) + (F(4)!)) \\ 48595 &:= (((((4! + F(8)) \times 5!) \times 9) - (5)) \\ 48596 &:= (((F(4)! \times ((8!/5) + F(9))) + F(6)) \\ 48599 &:= ((F(((F(4)! + 8)) \times (5! + 9)) - F(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48630 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 0 \\ 48631 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 1 \\ 48632 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 2 \\ 48633 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 3 \\ 48634 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 4 \\ 48635 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 5 \\ 48636 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 6 \\ 48637 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 7 \\ 48638 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 8 \\ 48639 &:= F(4!) + F(8 + 6) \times 3! + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48790 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 0 \\ 48791 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 1 \\ 48792 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 2 \\ 48793 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 3 \\ 48794 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 4 \\ 48795 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 5 \\ 48796 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 6 \\ 48797 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 7 \\ 48798 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 8 \\ 48799 &:= 4 \times F(F(8)) + 7! - F(9) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 48800 &:= F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 0 \\ 48801 &:= F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$48802 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 2$$

$$48803 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 3$$

$$48804 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 4$$

$$48805 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 5$$

$$48806 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 6$$

$$48807 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 7$$

$$48808 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 8$$

$$48809 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 80 + 9$$

$$48814 := -((((F(4))!)! + ((F(F(8)) + (-(((8 + 1))!)/(F(4))!))))))$$

$$48816 := ((4 \times F(F(8))) + (-8) + ((1 + 6))!)$$

$$48817 := ((4 \times F(F(8))) + (((8 - 1))! - (7)))$$

$$48822 := (((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((8 - F(2)))!) - 2)$$

$$48823 := (((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((8 - F(2)))!) - F(F(3)))$$

$$48824 := ((4 \times F(F(8))) + (8!/(2 \times 4)))$$

$$48825 := (F(4!) - ((F(8) \times (F((8/2)) - 5!))))$$

$$48827 := ((4 \times F(F(8))) + (F((8/2)) + 7!))$$

$$48832 := (((4 \times F(F(8))) + 8) + ((3! + F(2)))!)$$

$$48837 := (((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8)/3))!) + F(7))$$

$$48838 := (((((F(4!) + 8!) + F(F(8)))/F(3)) + (F(8)))$$

$$48843 := ((F(4) + ((8 \times 8))) \times (F(4)^{3!}))$$

$$48845 := (((4 \times F(F(8))) + (F(8))) + ((F(F(4)) + (5)))!)$$

$$48847 := (((((4 \times F(F(8))) + (F(8))) + F(F(4))) + (7!))$$

$$48848 := ((4! + (8!/8)) - (-4) \times F(F(8)))$$

$$48854 := ((F(4!) + 8) - (-F(8)) \times (5! - F(F(4))))$$

$$48862 := ((F(4!) - F(F(8))) + (8!/(6/2)))$$

$$48864 := (F(4!) + (((-8) + F(8)) \times F(6)) \times 4!)$$

$$48865 := (((((F(4))!)! \times (-8)) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) \times 5))$$

$$48867 := (F(4!) + (F(8) \times ((F(8) \times 6) - (7))))$$

$$48872 := (F(4!) + (-((8 + 8)) - (7!/(-2))))$$

$$48873 := ((F(4!) - (F(8))) + ((F(F(8)))/(-F(7))) \times (-3))$$

$$49024 := ((F((F(4))!))! - (-F(9)) \times (02^{F(F(4)!)}))$$

$$49028 := ((F(F(4)) \times F(9)) \times (0! + (-((2 - 8))!))$$

$$49030 := (F(F(4)) \times ((F(9) \times (0! + 3!!)) + 0!))$$

$$49032 := (F(F(4)) \times ((F(9) \times (0! + 3!!)) + 2))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49034 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times F(9)) \times (0! + 3!)) + (F(4))!) \\
 49036 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times F(9)) \times (0! + 3!)) + F(6)) \\
 49044 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((F(9) \times (0! + ((F(4))!)) + F((F(4))!))) \\
 49047 &:= -((F(4) \times ((F(9) + 0!) - (4^7))) \\
 49056 &:= (F(4!) + (F((9 - 0!) \times (5! + F(6)))) \\
 49064 &:= (((4! \times F((9 + 0!))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4) \\
 49074 &:= ((F(4))! \times (((F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(7))) + (4!))) \\
 49075 &:= (((((F(4))!)! + (F(9) + 0!)) \times (F(7) \times 5)) \\
 49077 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (((9 + 0!) \times F(F(7))) + 7)) \\
 49094 &:= (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-((F(9) - 0!) \times (F(9)^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 49094 &:= (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-((F(9) - 0!) \times (F(9)^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 49104 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 9)) - (1 + 0!))/4) \\
 49137 &:= ((F(4!)/(-9)) - (-F(13)) \times F(F(7))) \\
 49149 &:= (((-4!) + F(F((9 - 1))))/F(F(4))) \times 9) \\
 49157 &:= -(((F(4))! + ((-91) - 5!) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 49169 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((9 \times F(16)) - F(9))) \\
 49174 &:= (((4 + F(9)) \times F(F((1 \times 7)))) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 49176 &:= (F(4!) + ((9 \times (-1 + F(F(7)))) + (6!))) \\
 49178 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + ((9 \times (1 - F(F(7)))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 49203 &:= (F(4!) + (9!/(2^{0!+3!})) \\
 49206 &:= ((F(4))! \times (9 + (2^{F(0!+6)}))) \\
 49214 &:= ((F(4!) - F(9)) + (((2 + 1)!)! \times 4)) \\
 49223 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)/2) - F((F(2) + F(3!)))) \\
 49224 &:= ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F((9 \times 2))) - (((F(2) + (F(4))!))!)) \\
 49225 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)/2) - (2^5)) \\
 49226 &:= ((4! \times (F((F(9)/2)) - 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 49232 &:= ((F(F(4)) \times F(9)) \times ((2 + 3!) + 2)) \\
 49233 &:= (-4!) + ((-9) \times F(F(2^3)))/(-F(3)) \\
 49234 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((F(9) \times 2) \times ((3!)! + 4))) \\
 49236 &:= ((-4) + F((9 \times 2))) + (3!^6) \\
 49238 &:= ((F(4))! + (F(9) \times ((2 \times (3!)! + 8))) \\
 49242 &:= (-4!) + (9 \times ((2 + F(F(F((F(4))!))))/2)) \\
 49243 &:= ((F(4) + F((9 \times 2))) + ((F(4))!^{3!})) \\
 49244 &:= ((4 + F((9 \times 2))) + ((F(4))!^{F(4)!}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 49246 &:= (((F(4))! + F((9 \times 2))) + ((F(4))!^6)) \\
 49247 &:= (((F((4 + 9))^2) - F(F(4))) - (7!)) \\
 49248 &:= (F(4!) + ((9!/(2 + 4))/F(8))) \\
 49249 &:= -((F((F(4))!) - ((F(F((9 - F(2)))))/(-F(F(4)))) \times (-9))) \\
 49251 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)/2) - (5 + 1)) \\
 49252 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)/2) - (5 \times F(2))) \\
 49256 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9) - 2)/F((-5) + F(6))) \\
 49257 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9!)/(2 \times ((-5) + F(7))!) \\
 49258 &:= (((F(4!) \times F(9))/(2^5)) - 8) \\
 49259 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)/2) + F(F(-(5 - 9)))) \\
 49263 &:= ((F(4))! + ((-9) \times F(F((2 + 6))))/(-F(3))) \\
 49264 &:= ((4! + F((9 \times 2))) + (6^{F(4)!})) \\
 49265 &:= (((F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)/2) + F((6!/5!))) \\
 49266 &:= ((F(4!) \times F(9))/(26 + 6)) \\
 49267 &:= (((4! \times F((F(9)/2))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 7) \\
 49268 &:= (((4! \times F((F(9)/2))) - 6) + F(F(8))) \\
 49269 &:= (F(4) - (F(9) \times ((-2) \times 6!) - 9)) \\
 \\
 49270 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 0 \\
 49271 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 1 \\
 49272 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 2 \\
 49273 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 3 \\
 49274 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 4 \\
 49275 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 5 \\
 49276 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 6 \\
 49277 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 7 \\
 49278 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 8 \\
 49279 &:= F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9/2 + F(7) + 9 \\
 \\
 49280 &:= (((F((F(4))!))!)/(-9)) \times (-((2 + 8)) - 0!) \\
 49281 &:= (((F((F(4))!))!)/(-9)) \times (-2) + (8! + 1) \\
 49283 &:= (F((F(4))!) + (9 \times (2 - (F(F(8)))/(-F(3)))) \\
 49284 &:= (((F(4))! \times 9^2) + F(((8 - 4)!)) \\
 49285 &:= ((-((4! + 9)^2) + F(F(8))) \times 5) \\
 49286 &:= (((F((F(4))!))!)/(-9)) \times (-2) + ((8! + (6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 49287 := (((F(4) + F((9 × 2))) × F(8)) – 7!)
- 49288 := (((((F((F(4)!))!)/(-9)) × (-2)) – ((8) – 8!))
- 49289 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (9 + ((-2) × 8!)/(-9))))
- 49290 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/2) + (F(9) – 0!))
- 49291 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/2) + F((9 × 1)))
- 49292 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/2) + (F(9) + F(2)))
- 49293 := (((F((F(4)!)) + F(F((9 – F(2)))))) × (-9))/(-F(3)))
- 49294 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/2) + (F(9) + F(4)))
- 49294 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/2) + (F(9) + F(4)))
- 49296 := (((4! × F(9)) × (2 + 9)) + (F(6)!))
- 49323 := (-((F(4)!)) + (9 × ((F(F(F(3!)))/2) + F(3!))))
- 49326 := (-F(4) + (9 × ((F(F(F(3!)))/2) + F(6))))
- 49327 := (-F(F(4)) + (9 × ((F(F(3!))²) + (7!))))
- 49328 := (-F(F(F(4))) + (9 × ((F(F(F(3!)))/2) + 8)))
- 49329 := (F(4!) + (9 × 329))
- 49332 := (F(4) + (9 × (F(3!) – (F(F(F(3!)))/(-2))))
- 49333 := (4 + (9 × ((F(F(F(3!)))/F(3)) + F(3!)))
- 49334 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (-F(9)) + (F((3! + F(3!)) × 4!)))
- 49336 := (F(4!) + ((-((9! × 3!)) + (F(3!)!)/(-6!)))
- 49337 := (((F(F(4)) × F(9)) × (3!)! + F((F(3) × 7)))
- 49338 := (F(4!) + ((9 × 3!) × F((F(3) + 8)))
- 49339 := (F(F(F(4))) + (9 × ((F(F(F(3!)))/F(3)) + 9)))
- 49344 := (F(4!) + (((F(9) – 3) × 4) × 4!))
- 49346 := (((F(4) + F((F(9)/F(3)))) × 4!) + F(F(F(6))))
- 49348 := (-F((4 + 9)) + ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)}) + 8!))
- 49354 := (F(4!) + (F(9) + ((3 + 5!) × 4!)))
- 49356 := ((F(4))! × (F(9) + (F(3)^{5+F(6)})))
- 49358 := ((F(4!) – F(9)) + (((3!)!/5) × F(8)))
- 49360 := (F(4!) – (-F(9)) × (F((3 + F(6))) – 0!))
- 49362 := ((F(4) – (F(9) × (3! + 6!))) × (-2))
- 49363 := ((F(4!) + F(9)) + (3 × F((F(6) × F(3))))
- 49364 := ((F(F(4)) × (F(9) × (3! + 6!))) – 4)
- 49365 := (F(4!) + (9 × (-3) – ((F(6)!)/(-5!))))
- 49366 := -((F(F(4)) + ((F(9) × F(3)) × (-6) – 6!)))

- 49370 := ((F(F((F(4)!)) × (F((9 × F(3))) - F(F(7)))) - 0!)
- 49371 := (F(F((F(4)!)) × (F((9 × F(3))) - F(F((7 × 1))))))
- 49372 := ((F(F((F(4)!)) × (F((9 × F(3))) - F(F(7)))) + F(2))
- 49373 := (F(4!) + ((F(9) × F(-(F(3) - F(7)))) - F(F(3!))))
- 49374 := ((F(4)! × (F(9) + ((F(3)^{F(7)}) + F(4))))
- 49376 := -(((4! - ((F(9)^{F(3)}) + 7!)) × F(6))
- 49383 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/F(3)) + (F(8) × 3!))
- 49384 := (((4 × (F(9)³)) + 8!)/4)
- 49385 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9)/F(3)) + (8 + 5!))
- 49386 := (F(4!) + ((F((9 + 3)) × F(8)) - (6)))
- 49387 := (F(4!) + ((F(9) × F((3 + 8))) - (7)))
- 49389 := (-F(4) + ((-F(9) + 3!!) × (8 × 9)))
- 49391 := ((F((F(4)!)) × ((-F(9) + 3!!) × 9)) - 1)
- 49392 := (F(4!) + (9!/((-((3 - 9)) - F(2))!))
- 49393 := (F(4!) + ((-F(9) + F((F(3) + 9)))^{F(3)}))
- 49394 := ((-((4 - 93)) × F(9)) + F(4!))
- 49394 := ((-((4 - 93)) × F(9)) + F(4!))
- 49395 := (F(4!) + ((9/3) + (9!/5!)))
- 49396 := (F((4 + 9)) × ((3! × F(9)) + F(6)))
- 49397 := (F(4!) + (F((F(9) - ((3 × 9)))) × F(F(7))))
- 49398 := ((F(4)! + ((9!/(3! + F(9))) + 8!))
- 49407 := ((F((F(4)!))! + (((F(9) + (4)) + 0!) × F(F(7))))
- 49413 := ((F(4!) + ((9!/((4 + 1)!))) + F(F(3!)))
- 49414 := (((((F(4)! - 9!)/(-F(4)!)) - F(F(F((F((1 × 4))!))))))
- 49415 := -((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + ((-9!)/(F(4)! - (1 - 5!))))
- 49419 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + F(9))/F(F(4))) + 1) × 9)
- 49424 := (F((F(4)!)) × (F(9) - (-4! × (2^{F(F(4)!)}))))
- 49426 := ((F(4!) + F(9)) + (F((4!/2)) × F(F(6))))
- 49428 := (F(4!) + ((F(9) × ((4 + 2)!)/8))
- 49434 := (((F(F(4))⁹) × (F(4)! - 3!) + F(4!))
- 49435 := (((F(F((F(4)!)) + (9!/(F(4)!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) - 5!)
- 49436 := (F(F(4)) × (F(9) × ((4 + 3) + 6!)))
- 49437 := (F(F(F(4))) + ((F(9) × F(F(4))) × ((3!) + 7)))
- 49438 := ((F(4!)/(-9)) + ((4^{F(3!)}) - F(F(8))))

$$49440 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 0$$

$$49441 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 1$$

$$49442 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 2$$

$$49443 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 3$$

$$49444 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 4$$

$$49445 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 5$$

$$49446 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 6$$

$$49447 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 7$$

$$49448 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 8$$

$$49449 := F(F(4))^9 \times F(4)! + F(4!) + 9$$

$$49452 := (-F(4!)) + (F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) \times (5!/2))$$

$$49453 := ((-(4! - 9!)) + (F((F(4)!)^5)))/F(3!)$$

$$49454 := (-F(F(4))) + ((9! + (F((F(4)!)^5)))/F((F(4)!)))$$

$$49455 := (F(4!) - ((F(9) + ((4 - (5^5))))))$$

$$49457 := (-F((4 + 9))) + ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) \times 5) - (7!)))$$

$$49458 := (F(F(4)) + ((-9!) - (F((F(4)!)^5)))/(-8))$$

$$49459 := (F(4!) + (((9 - 4)^5) - F(9)))$$

$$49462 := (F(4!) + (F(9) \times (F((F(4) + F(6))) + 2)))$$

$$49464 := (4! \times (((-9) - 4!) + 6!) \times F(4))$$

$$49466 := ((4! \times (F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) + F(6))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$49467 := (F(4!) + (((9 + 4!) - (F(6)!)/(-F(7))))$$

$$49472 := (F((F(4)!) \times ((9^4) - F((7 \times 2))))$$

$$49473 := (((F(4)!) \times F(9)) + F(4)) \times (F(F(7)) + 3!)$$

$$49474 := ((F(4)^9) + ((4! + (7))^{F(4)}))$$

$$49476 := (((F(4)!) \times 9) + (F(F(4))^{F(7)})) \times 6$$

$$49477 := (((4! \times 9) \times (-4) + F(F(7)))) + F(7)$$

$$49478 := (((4 + F(9)) \times (F((F(4)!) + F(F(7)))) + 8!)$$

$$49483 := (F(4!) + ((F(9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times F((8 + 3))))$$

$$49484 := ((F((F(4)!) + ((9! \times F(4)))))/F(8) + F(F(F(4))))$$

$$49488 := ((F(4!) + ((9 - F(F(4))))!) - (8!/F(8)))$$

$$49494 := (F(4!) + ((9 + (F(F(4))^9)) \times (F(4)!)))$$

$$49494 := (F(4!) + ((9 + (F(F(4))^9)) \times (F(4)!)))$$

$$49495 := -((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((9!/(F(4)!) - (F(9) + (5))))))$$

- 49496 := (F(4!) + (F(9) × (-(4 - 96))))
- 49498 := ((4 × ((9!/4!) - 9)) - F(F(8)))
- 49504 := ((F(F(4)) × F(9)) × (F((5 + 0!)) + ((F(4))!))
- 49507 := (-((F(4) - F(9))) × F(((5 - 0!) + F(7))))
- 49513 := -(((F(F((F(4))!)) + (9!/(-5 + 1)))) + F(F(F(3!))))
- 49514 := (((F((F(4))!) - F(9)) × (-5! + 1)) + F(4!))
- 49524 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((9! - (5!/2))/(F(4))!)))
- 49526 := -(((F((F(4))!) + (9!/(-5 - F(2)))) + F(F(F(6))))
- 49527 := (F(4!) + (F(9) + (5⁻²⁺⁷)))
- 49528 := -((((F(4))! + (9!/(-5 - F(2)))) + F(F(8))))
- 49532 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((9!/((5 - F(3))!) - 2)))
- 49533 := (((((F(4))! - 9!) × (-5!))/(3!)! - F(F(F(3!))))
- 49534 := (((((F((F(4))!)!)/F(F((9 - 5)))) - F(F(F(3!))) + (F((F(4))!))!))
- 49536 := (4! × (((9 + 5!) × F(3)) × F(6)))
- 49537 := (((F(4))!)! + ((9!/(-5)) + F((F(3) × F(7)))))
- 49538 := ((4! + ((9! - 5!)/3!)) - F(F(8)))
- 49542 := ((F(4))! - (((F(9) - 5!) × (4!²))))
- 49543 := (((((F(4))!)! + (9⁵)) + ((F(4))!)! - F(F(F(3!))))
- 49544 := (F((F(4))!) - (((F(9) - 5!) × 4!) × 4!))
- 49545 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) + (9 × 5!)) × 45)
- 49546 := -((((F((F(4))!) - ((9! + 5!)/(F(4))!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 49547 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (((9! + 5!)/(F(4))! - 7)))
- 49548 := ((F(4)!)/(-9)) - (5 × ((F(4))! - F(F(8))))
- 49553 := ((F(4)!)/(-9)) + (-5 × (5 - F(F(F(3!))))
- 49554 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((9! + 5!)/((5 - F(F(4)))))!))
- 49555 := ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (9 × (5 - 5!))) × 5)
- 49560 := ((F((F(4))!)! + ((F(9) + 5!) × 60))
- 49562 := (F(4!) + (F((F(9)/F((-5) + F(6)))) × 2))
- 49563 := (F(4!) + (9 × (-5) + (6!/F(3))))
- 49564 := (F(4!) + (F(9) × (5 + F((F(6) + F(4))))))
- 49567 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (((9! + 5!)/6) + F(7)))
- 49568 := ((F((F(4))!) × (F(9)^{F(-5+F(6))})) + 8!)
- 49569 := ((F(4)!)/(-9)) - ((-5) × F(F(F(6)))) + 9)
- 49574 := (F(4!) + ((9 + 5) × (F(F(7)) - 4)))
- 49576 := (4 × (F(9) - ((5! × F(F(7))) - (F(6))!)))

- 49578** := $((F(4!)/(-9)) - (-5 \times F((F(7) + 8))))$
49579 := $((F(4!) + F(9)) - ((-5!) - F(F(7))) \times 9)$
49580 := $((F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(9-5)} + ((8! - 0!)))$
49581 := $((F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(9-5)} + ((8 \times 1)!))$
49582 := $((F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(9-5)} + ((8! + F(2))))$
49583 := $((F(4!)/(-9)) - (-5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(3))))$
49584 := $-(((4! \times F(9)) + ((5 \times 8!)/(-4))))$
49586 := $((F(4!)/(-9)) - ((-5 \times F(F(8))) - F(6)))$
49593 := $((F(4!) - 9) + ((5! + F(9)) \times F(F(3))))$
49594 := $(F(4!) + ((95 \times F(9)) - (4)))$
49594 := $(F(4!) + ((95 \times F(9)) - (4)))$
49596 := $(F(4!) + ((9!/5!) - (F(9) \times (-6))))$
49598 := $(F(4!) + (95 \times F((9!/8!))))$
49604 := $(((((F((F(4)!))!)! - (-F(9)) \times F(F(F(6)))))) - ((0! + F((F(4)!))!))!)$
49608 := $(F(4!) + (9!/(((6 - 0)! - 8)))$
49612 := $(((((F(4)!))!)! + (F(9) \times ((6! - 1) \times 2)))$
49615 := $((F((F(4)!))!)! + (F(9) + (F(F(6))^{F(-1+5)})))$
49623 := $(((((F(4)!))!)! + (9 \times F(F(F(6)))))/2) + 3!$
49624 := $((F((F(4)!)) \times (-F(9) + (F(F(6))^2))) + F(4!))$
49625 := $((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F(9) + F((F(6) \times 2)))) \times 5)$
49629 := $((4! + (9 \times F(F(6)))) \times F(F(-(2 - 9))))$
49632 := $(F(4!) + (96 \times F((3^2))))$
49633 := $(((((F(4)!))!)! + 9!)/6 - F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(F(3!))))$
49634 := $(((((F(4)!)) \times (-F(9) \times F(6))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F((F(4)!))!))$
49636 := $(F(-(4! - F(9))) + ((F(F(6))^3) + (F(6)!)))$
49637 := $(F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (-9 \times ((F(F(6)) + 3!!) - (7!))))$
49638 := $((F(4!) - (F(9) - 6!)) + F((-3) + F(8)))$
49640 := $((F((F(4)!))!)! + (F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) \times 40))$
49644 := $(((((F(4)!)) \times (F(9) + (F(6)^{F(4)}))) + F(4!))$
49646 := $(((((F(4)!))!)! + 9!)/6 - F((F(4)!)) - F(F(F(6))))$
49647 := $((-((4! + 9)) + (F(6)!)) - (((F(4)!))!) \times (-F(7)))$
49648 := $-(((F(4)!)) - (((9! + 6!)/(F(4)!)) - F(F(8))))$
49649 := $((F((F(4)!))!)! + (F(9) + ((F(F(6))^{F(4)} + F(9))))$
49652 := $-((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (((9!/(-6)) - 5!) + 2)))$

- 49653 := (((((F(4))! - 9!)/(-6)) + 5!) - F(F(F(3!))))
49654 := (((((F(4))!)! + 9!)/6) - F(F((5 + F(4))))
49656 := -(4!) - ((9 × F(F(6))) - 5!) × (-6!))
49657 := -(4! + 9) + ((F(F(F(6))) × 5) - (7!))
49658 := (((4! + 9!)/6) + 5!) - F(F(8))
49662 := (F(4!) + (9 × (6 - (6!/(-2))))
49663 := (F(4!) + ((-9) + 6!) + F((6 × 3)))
49665 := (F(4) × ((9!/F(F(6))) - ((6! + (5))))
49666 := (((-F(4)) - F((9 + F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6))!
49667 := -(((F(4) + (-9) × F(6)) × 6!) + F(7))
49668 := -(((F(4))! - (F(9) × ((6! + 6!) + F(8))))
49669 := -((F(F(4)) + (9 - (6! × 69))))
49670 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (-9) + ((6! × F(7)) - 0!))
49671 := (F(4) × ((F(9) × (6! - F(F(7)))) - 1))
49672 := (((F(4) × F(9)) × (6! - F(F(7)))) - 2)
49673 := (((F(F(4)) × (F(9) × 6!)) - 7) + 3!!)
49674 := (((F(4))! × F(9)) × (6! - F(F(7))))/F(F(4))
49675 := (((F(4))!)! × (-9) - (-6) × F(7)) - (5)
49676 := -(4) + (((9!/F(6)) + 7!) - 6!))
49677 := ((-((4 - 9)) × F(F(F(6)))) - ((7! + F(7))))
49678 := -((F(F(4)) - (((9 - 6))!)! × F(7)) + 8!))
49693 := (((F(4))! + F((9 + F(6)))) × (F(9) - 3))
49694 := ((F(4!) - F(9)) + ((F(6))!/(9 + F(4))))
49694 := ((F(4!) - F(9)) + ((F(6))!/(9 + F(4))))
49698 := (F(4) × ((9!/F(F(6))) - ((F(9) × F(8))))
49707 := (F(F((F(4))!)) × ((F(9) × 70) - F(7))
49714 := (((((F(4))!)! × F(9)) + (F((F(7) + 1)))) × F(F(4))
49725 := -(((F(4))!)! + ((-9) + (7! × (-2))) × 5))
49726 := -((F(4) - (97²)) + (F(6))!)
49727 := (F(4!) - (((F(9) + (7))²) - 7!))
49728 := (F(4!) + ((-9) + (F(7)²)) × F(8))
49730 := (((4! × 9) + (7))^{F(3)} + 0!)
49732 := (F(4!) + ((F(9) + ((7 - 3))!)²))
49734 := (F(4!) + (((9 + 7!) × F(3))/F(4))
49736 := (F(4!) + (((F(9) × F(7)) - F(F(3!))) × F(6))

- 49737** := $(F(4!) + (9 + ((7!/(-3)) + 7!)))$
49738 := $((((F(4))! \times (F(9) + (7! \times F(3)))) - F(F(8))))$
49743 := $(F(4!) + ((9 + ((7 - 4)!)^3))$
49744 := $((- (4!) \times ((- (9) \times F(F(7))) + (4!))) - F((F(4))!))$
49745 := $((F(-((F(4) - 9))))! + (F(7) \times (((F(4))!)! + (5))))$
49746 := $((- (4!) \times ((- (9) \times F(F(7))) + (4!))) - 6)$
49747 := $(4 + (9 \times ((- (F(F(7))) + ((F(4))!)! + (7!))))$
49748 := $((((F(F(4)) \times (F(9) + 7!)) - ((F(4))!)! + 8!))$
49749 := $(F(F((F(4))!)) \times ((9 \times F(F(7))) - (F((F(4))!) \times (-F(9))))$
49750 := $((F((F(4))!) + (F((9 + 7)))) \times 50)$
49752 := $(- (4!) \times ((- (9) \times F(F(7))) + ((5 - F(2))!))$
49753 := $(((((F(4))!)! - 9) \times (-7)) - (- (5) \times F(F(F(3!))))$
49754 := $((F((F(4))!)! + (9 - (F(7) \times (-5) - ((F(4))!)!))))$
49755 := $((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((- (F(9)) + F(F(7))) \times 5)) \times 5)$
49758 := $(F(4) \times (((F(9) + F(7)) \times 5!) + F(F(8))))$
49760 := $(F(4!) + ((9 \times F((-7) + F(F(6)))) - 0!))$
49761 := $(F(4!) + (9 \times F((7 + 6) + 1)))$
49762 := $(F(4!) + ((9 \times F((-7) + F(F(6)))) + F(2)))$
49763 := $(F(4!) + ((9 \times F((-7) + F(F(6)))) + F(3)))$
49764 := $(F(4!) + ((9 + (7!/6)) \times 4))$
49765 := $((- (((F(4))! + F((9 + 7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5)$
49766 := $(- (4) + ((- ((9! - 7!)) - (F(6))!) / (-F(6))))$
49767 := $- (((((4! - 9!) + 7!) / F(6)) - 7!))$
49768 := $- ((F(F(4)) - ((- ((9! - 7!)) - (F(6))!) / (-8))))$
49770 := $(F(4!) + (9 \times (F((7 + 7) + 0!)))$
49771 := $((((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(9)) - F(7)) \times 71)$
49773 := $(((4! + 9!) - (7! \times (-7))) / F(3!))$
49774 := $((((4! - (F(9) \times (-7))) \times F(7)) + F(4!))$
49776 := $((F(4))! + (((9! - (7! \times (-7))) / F(6))))$
49777 := $(F(4!) + (((F((-9) + F(7))))!)! - F(F(7)) \times 7)$
49778 := $(F((F(4))!) + ((9! - (7! \times (-7))) / 8))$
49786 := $((((F(4) + 9) \times (7! + F(8))) - F(F(F(6))))$
49787 := $(F(4!) + (((9 + F(F(7))) + (F(8))) \times F(7)))$
49790 := $- ((F((4! - 9)) - (7! \times (9 + 0!)))$
49797 := $((F((F(4))!)! + ((9^{F(F(7)-9)}) \times F(7)))$

- 49824 := (F(4!) + (((9 × 8) × 2) × 4!))
- 49826 := (((F(4))! × (9 × ((8 - 2))!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 49833 := (F(4!) + (9 × (F((8 + 3!)) + F(3!))))
- 49834 := (((-(4! × F(9))) + F(F(8))) × 3! - F(F(F((F(4))!))))
- 49836 := (((F(4))!)! × F(9)) + ((F(F(8)) × 3!) - (F(6))!))
- 49837 := ((-(4 - 9)) × F(F(8))) - (F(F(3!)) × F(F(7)))
- 49838 := (((F(F(4)) × -(F(9) × F(8)))) + (F(3!)!) + F(F(8)))
- 49839 := (((F((F(4))!) - 9!)/(-8)) - ((F(3!)!)/(-9)))
- 49840 := (((F((F(4))!)!)/9) + (8! + (((F(4))! + 0!)!))
- 49842 := (((((F(4))!)! × F(9)) + ((F(8)^{F(F(4))}))) × 2)
- 49844 := ((F(F(4)) × F(9)) × (F((F(8)/F(4))) + ((F(4))!))
- 49845 := (F(4!) + ((9 × (8 - F(4!)))/(-5!)))
- 49848 := (((F(4))! × (-9) + F((F(8) - (4)))) + 8!)
- 49857 := (-F(4) + (((F(9) + F(F(8))) × 5) - (7!)))
- 49862 := ((F(4!) - F(9)) + (8 × (F(F(6))²)))
- 49863 := (F(4!) + (F((F(9) - F(8))) × (F(F(6)) - 3!)))
- 49866 := (((F(4))! × (F((9 + 8)) - (6))) + (F(6))!)
- 49867 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) + ((-9) × (F(8) + F(6))) × F(F(7))))
- 49868 := -((((F(4))! × F((F(9) - F(8)))) - (F(6))! - F(F(8))))
- 49870 := (F(4!) + (F(9) × ((8 × F(7)) - 0!)))
- 49873 := (((49 - 8) × F(F(7))) + (F(3!)!))
- 49874 := ((F((F(4))!)! + (F(9) × ((F(8) × F(7)) + F((F(4))!))))
- 49875 := (((F(4))!)! - (F(9) + F(8))) × 75)
- 49888 := (F(4!) + ((F(9) + F(8)) × (8 × 8)))
- 49893 := (((F(4))! × F((9 + 8)) - 9) + (F(3!)!))
- 49896 := (((4! + 9) × F(8)) × 9) × F(6)
- 49923 := ((F(4)⁹) - ((9!/(-2))/3!))
- 49924 := ((F((F(4))!)! + ((9 + F((9 + 2)))^{F(F(4))}))
- 49930 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (9 + (-9) × F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))))
- 49932 := (F(4!) + (99 × (3!²)))
- 49933 := (((F(4) + F(9))^{9/3}) - 3!)
- 49936 := (((4 × F((9 + 9))) - 3!) + (F(6))!)
- 49938 := (((4! × 99) + F(3)) × F(8))
- 49939 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (9 × F(((9 + F(3)) + 9))))

- 49943 := (((((F(4))!)! - F(9)) - ((9 × F(F(F((F(4))!)))))/(-F(3))))
- 49944 := ((F(F((F(4))!)) × F((9 + 9))) - ((F(4))! × ((F(4))!))
- 49946 := (((((F(4) + 9))!)/(-9!)) + (F((F(4))!))! + F(F(F(6))))
- 49947 := (((((F(4))!)! × (F(9) + F(9))) + (F((F(4) + F(7))))))
- 49948 := -((((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - 9) + (-9) × F(-(F(F(F(4))) - (F(8))))))
- 49959 := ((F((F(4))!))! + (9 × ((9 × 5!) - 9)))
- 49967 := -((F(-((F((F(4))! - F(9)))) + ((F(9) × 6!) × (-7))))
- 49968 := (F((F(4))!) × (-9) × ((F(9) - 6!) - 8))
- 49972 := (F(4!) + (F(9) × (F(9) + 72)))
- 49973 := -((F(-((F((F(4))! - F(9)))) - (((F(9) × 7!) + 3!))))
- 49975 := ((-4!) - ((-9) - F(9)) × F(F(7))) × 5
- 49976 := (F(4!) + ((9 + (F(9) × F(7))) × F(6)))
- 50328 := (((5 + 0!)³) × F(F(-(F(2) - 8))))
- 50333 := (5 + (F(F((0! + 3!))) × (3!³)))
- 50344 := (-5!) + (((0! + 3)^{F(4)!}) + F(4!))
- 50374 := (((5 × ((0! + 3!))!) - F(7)) × F(F(4)))
- 50375 := (-5) × (((0 - F(3)) × 7!) + (5))
- 50376 := -((((5 - 0!))! - ((F(3) × 7!)) - (F(6))!))
- 50384 := (((5 × ((0! + 3!))!) - 8) × F(F(4)))
- 50387 := ((5! × ((-0!) + F(F(3!))) × F(8)) - F(7))
- 50394 := (((-5) - 0!) - (F(3!))!) + (9!/4)
- 50396 := ((-5) + 0!) + (((F(3!))! + 9!)/F(6))
- 50397 := -((F((5 - 0!)) + ((F(F(3)) + 9) × (-7!))))
- 50398 := -((F(F((5 - 0!))) - (((F(3!))! + 9!)/8)))
- 50400 := ((5 × ((0! + (F(4))!))!) × (0! + 0!))
- 50402 := (((5 × ((0! + (F(4))!))!) + 0!) × 2)
- 50405 := (((((F((5 + 0!)))!)/4) + 0!) × 5)
- 50405 := (((((F((5 + 0!)))!)/4) + 0!) × 5)
- 50414 := (((5! - 0!) × F((F((F(4))! + 1))) + F(4!))
- 50424 := (((5 × ((0! + (F(4))!))!) × 2) + (4!))
- 50425 := (-5) × (((0! + (F(4))!))! × (-2) - (5))
- 50425 := (-5) × ((-2) × (((F(4))! + 0!))! - (5))
- 50428 := ((-((5! + 0!)) + F(4!)) + F((-2) + F(8)))
- 50432 := (((5 - 0!)^{F(F(4)!)}) - (F(3!))!) × 2

- 50442 := (((5 × ((0! + (F(4)!))!) + F(F((F(4)!))) × 2)
- 50443 := (((5 - 0!)^{F(4)!} + F(4!)) - F(F(3!)))
- 50444 := ((5! × F((0! + F((F(4)!)))) - (4 - F(4!)))
- 50447 := ((5! - 0!) + (((F(4)!^{F(4)}) × F(F(7))))
- 50448 := ((5! × F((0! + F((F(4)!)))) + (F((F(4) × 8))))
- 50460 := (((5! + 0!) + ((F(4)!))!) × 60)
- 50462 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + ((4⁶) - 2))
- 50463 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + ((4⁶) - F(F(3))))
- 50464 := (((5 - 0!)^{F(4)!} + (F((6 × 4))))
- 50470 := (((5 × 0!)! + ((F(4)!))!) × 70)
- 50484 := ((-((5! - 0!)) + ((F(4)!))!) × 84)
- 50494 := ((5! × (F(F(04))⁹)) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))
- 50543 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + ((F((-5 + 4!)) - 3!)))
- 50544 := ((-5) + F(((0 - 5) + 4!))) + F(4!))
- 50546 := (-(((5 + 0!)! - ((5 + F(4)))!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 50549 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + (F((-5 × F(4) + F(9))))
- 50554 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + (5 + F((-5 + 4!))))
- 50584 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + (5! + (8⁴)))
- 50625 := ((5!/F(06))^{-F(2)+5})
- 50634 := ((5 × F(F(F(06)))) - (F(3!)⁴))
- 50646 := (((5!/F(06))⁴) + F(F(6)))
- 50653 := (((5 - 0!) × F(6) + (5))³)
- 50656 := (((F((5 + 0!)))! + F(F(F(6)))) - F((5!/F(6))))
- 50664 := ((((-5) + 0!) + 6!) × 6) + F(4!))
- 50666 := ((5! + F(F(F(06)))) + ((F(6)! - (6!)))
- 50667 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) - (F(F(6) + (6! - 7!)))
- 50673 := (((5! × (-0!) + F(F(6)))) + F(7)) × F(F(3!)))
- 50679 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) - ((6! - 7!) + 9))
- 50694 := (((50 + F(F(6))) × F(9)) × F(F((F(4)!)))
- 50697 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) - ((6! - 9) - 7!))
- 50744 := ((5! - 0!) + ((F(7) + F(F(4)))⁴))
- 50766 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) - ((F(7) + 6!) × (-6)))
- 50778 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) - ((7! × (-7))/8))
- 50782 := (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + ((F(F(7)) + F((F(8) - 2))))

$$\begin{aligned} 50820 &:= (((5! + 0!) \times F(8)) \times 20) \\ 50832 &:= ((5! + F(F(-(0! - 8)))) \times F((3! \times 2))) \\ 50848 &:= -((5! - (((0! + F(8))^{F(4)} + 8!))) \\ 50866 &:= ((-(50 \times 8)) + (F(6))!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 50869 &:= (F(((5 - 0!)!) - (-F(8)) + ((F(6))!/(-9)))) \\ 50973 &:= (((((5 + 0!)!) - F((9 + F(7)))) \times (-3)) \\ 50992 &:= (F(((5 - 0!)!) + ((F(9) + F(9))^2)) \\ 50993 &:= (((F(F((5 - 0!))) + 9!)/F(9)) + (F(3!)!) \\ 51033 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - F(F((0! + 3!)))) + (F(3!)!) \\ 51135 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + (1 - 3!)) \times 5) \\ 51144 &:= ((-5) + (F(11) \times 4!)) \times 4! \\ 51145 &:= (((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - 1) + (F((F(4))!)!) - 5!) \\ 51146 &:= ((-5!) + F(F(((1 + 1) \times 4))) + (F(6))!) \\ 51148 &:= ((-(5! - (1 + 1))) + (F((F(4))!)!) + F(F(8))) \\ 51236 &:= (((-5) \times ((1 + 2)!) + (F(3!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 51243 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + ((F(2) - 4!)) + (F(3!)!) \\ 51244 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - (-2 + 4!)) + (F((F(4))!)!) \\ 51246 &:= (((F((5 + 1))!) + F(2)) - F(F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 51253 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - F((2 + 5))) + (F(3!)!) \\ 51256 &:= (F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + (-((2 \times 5)) + (F(6))!) \\ 51258 &:= (((F((5 + 1))!) - F((F(2) + (5)))) + F(F(8))) \\ 51260 &:= (((-5) + (F(((1 + 2)!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 0!) \\ 51261 &:= ((-5) + (F(((1 + 2)!)!) + F(F(F((6 \times 1)))) \\ 51262 &:= (F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - ((2 - (F(6))!) + 2)) \\ 51263 &:= (((F((5 + 1))!) + F(F((2 + 6)))) - 3) \\ 51264 &:= (((5 - 1)!)^2 \times F((F(6) + F(4)))) \\ 51265 &:= ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - F(2)) + (F((6!/5!))!) \\ 51266 &:= (F(((5 \times (1 + 2)) + 6)) + (F(6))!) \\ 51267 &:= (((F((5 + 1))!) + F(2)) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \\ 51268 &:= ((F(F((5 - 1))) + F(F((2 + 6)))) + 8!) \\ 51271 &:= ((5 + (F(((1 + 2)!)!) + (F(F((7 + 1)))) \\ 51273 &:= ((F(F(((5 - 1) \times 2))) + 7) + (F(3!)!) \\ 51274 &:= (((F((5 + 1))!) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))) + F((F(4))!) \\ 51278 &:= (((F((5 + 1))!) - ((F(2) - F(7)))) + F(F(8))) \\ 51283 &:= (((5 + 12) + F(F(8))) + (F(3!)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 51286** := (((5!/((1+2)!) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!)
51288 := (((((5-1)!) - 2) + 8!) + F(F(8)))
51298 := (((F((5+1)))! + (-2) + F(9))) + F(F(8)))
51316 := (((51 + (F(3!)!) - 1) + F(F(F(6))))
51317 := ((51 + (F(3!)!) + (F(F((1+7))))))
51318 := ((51 + (F(3!)!) - (-1 - F(F(8))))
51333 := (((5! + F((1 + F(F(3!)))))) - ((3!)!) × 3)
51335 := ((-51) + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(3!)! + 5!))
51336 := ((51 × (3!³)) + (F(6))!)
51338 := (((((5-1)!) × 3) + (F(3!)!) + F(F(8)))
51357 := ((-51) + F((-((F(F(3)) - 5))))!) + (7!)
51364 := (((5! - 1) - F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(4))!))!
51365 := ((F(F(F((5+1)))) + (F(3!)!) - ((F(F(6)) - 5!)))
51366 := (((5! + 1) - F(F(3!))) + (F(6))!) + F(F(F(6)))
51368 := (((51 × F(3)) + (F(6))!) + F(F(8)))
51374 := (-((F((5+1) + 3)) - 7!)) + F(4!)
51378 := ((-((5! + 1)) + (F(3!)!) + ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))))))
51379 := ((5 + F(((1+3)!)!)) + (7! - F(9)))
51383 := (((5! - 1) + (F(3!)!) + ((F(F(8)) - F(3))))
51384 := ((5! + (F(((1 × 3)!)!))!) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))))))
51385 := (((51 - 3!!) + F(F(8))) × 5)
51386 := ((5! + F((13+8))) + (F(6))!)
51387 := (F(((5 - (1³))!) - ((F(8) - 7!)))
51388 := (((5! + F((1 × 3))) + 8!) + F(F(8)))
51394 := (((-5) + ((1+3!)!) - 9) + F(4!))
51395 := ((F(F(F((5+1)))) + (F(3!)!) + (9 + 5!))
51396 := (((5! + 1) + (F(3!)!) + 9) + F(F(F(6))))
51397 := (F(((5-1)!) - ((F(3) + 9) - 7!))
51399 := ((F(((5-1)!) + (-((F(3) - 9))!) - 9)
51403 := ((-5) + F(((1 × 4)!)!)) + ((0! + 3!)!)
51404 := ((-5) + ((1 + (F(4)!)!)!)) + (0! + F(4!))
51406 := ((F(((5-1)!) - F(F(4))) + ((0! + (6))!)
51407 := ((F(((5+1) × 4)) - 0!) + 7!)
51408 := (F(((5-1)!) + (-(((4 × 0)!) - 8))!)
51413 := ((5 + F(((1 × 4)!)!)) + ((1 + 3!)!))

- 51414 := ((5 + ((1 + (F(4))!))!) + (1 + F(4!)))
 51416 := ((F((5 + 1)) + F(4!)) + ((1 + 6))!)
 51417 := ((F((5 + 1)) + F(4!)) + (1 + 7!))
 51427 := ((F(F((5 + 1))) + F(4!)) + (-(2) + 7!))
 51429 := ((F(F((5 + 1))) + F(4!)) + (-((2 - 9)))!)
 51432 := (((5 - 1))! + F(4!)) + ((3! + F(2)))!
 51434 := (((5 + ((1 + (F(4))!))!) + F(F(3!))) + F(4!))
 51436 := ((5 × F((1 + F((F(4))!)))) + ((F(3!)! + F(F(F(6)))))
 51437 := (((F(F((5 + 1))) + F(4!)) + F(3!)) + (7!))
 51444 := (((F(((5 - 1))!)/F((F(4))!)) - ((F(4))!)) + F(4!))
 51446 := ((F((5 + 1)))! + (((F(4))!)/4 + F(F(F(6)))))
 51447 := ((5 + F((1 + F((F(4))!)))) + (F(4!) + (7!)))
 51464 := (((F((5 + 1)))!)/F(F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 4
 51467 := ((51 + F(4!)) + ((F(6) + 7!)))
 51478 := ((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + (F((F(4))!))!) + (F(F(7)) - (F(8))))
 51479 := -((F(F(F((5 - 1)))) - ((-F(4) × (F(7))!)/(-9!)))
 51494 := ((5! + ((1 + (F(4))!))!) + (-F(9) + F(4!)))
 51497 := ((F(((5 - 1))!)) + F((F(F(4)) + 9))) + (7!))
 51527 := (F(((5 - 1))!)) + (((5! - F(2)) + 7!))
 51528 := ((F(((5 - 1))!)) + 5!) + (-((F(2) - 8)))!
 51536 := (F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - (F((5!/3!)) × (-6)))
 51595 := (-5) × (1 - ((5! - F(9)) × 5!))
 51597 := -(((F((5 - 1))⁵) + (9!/(-7)))
 51626 := (F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - ((6!/(-2)) - (F(6))!))
 51643 := (((F((5 + 1)))! + F(F(F(6)))) + F(((F(4))! + F(3!))))
 51648 := (((5 - 1))! × ((6! × F(4)) - 8))
 51680 := (F((5 + F((1 + 6)))) × (F(8) - 0!))
 51696 := ((F(F((5 - 1))) - (6!)) × (-9) × F(6))
 51737 := ((F((5 + 1)))! + ((7^{F(3)}) × F(F(7))))
 51744 := (((-5) × ((1 + 7))!) + F(4!)) / (-F(4))
 51763 := (((5! + F((1 + F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(3!)!))
 51783 := ((517 + F(F(8))) + (F(3!)!))
 51788 := -(((5! + 1) × (F(7) - (F(8) × F(8))))
 51833 := (F(((5 - 1))!)) + ((F(F(8))/F(3)) - F(3!))
 51834 := (((51 + F(8)) × (3!)!) - (F(4))!))

$$\begin{aligned}
 51835 &:= (-5) + (((1+8)!/(F(3) + (5)))) \\
 51837 &:= ((-F(F((5+1)))) + ((8 + F(F(3))))!)/7 \\
 51839 &:= -(F(F(F((5-1)))) - ((-8) \times (3!)! \times (-9))) \\
 51862 &:= ((F(((5-1)!)) + (F(8))) - (F(F(F(6)))/(-2))) \\
 51864 &:= (((51 + F(8)) \times 6!) + 4!) \\
 51866 &:= (((-5!) + F(F((1 \times 8)))) + (6!)) + (F(6))! \\
 51870 &:= (((5+1)! + F(8)) \times 70) \\
 51876 &:= (((F((5+1)))! + F(F(8))) + F((7 + F(6)))) \\
 51879 &:= (5 + (((1+8)!/7) + F(9))) \\
 51963 &:= (5! - ((1 - (-9!)/F(F(6)))) \times (-3)) \\
 51986 &:= (((5 + (1^9))! + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!) \\
 52038 &:= (((5! - 2) \times F(F((03)!))) \times F(8)) \\
 52128 &:= (F(((5 - F(2)))!)) + (((1+2)! \times 8)) \\
 52136 &:= (F(((5 - F(2)))!)) - ((-1 - 3!) \times F(6)) \\
 52146 &:= ((5 \times F(21)) - F((4! - (6)))) \\
 52164 &:= ((F(((5^2) - 1))/F(6)) + F(4!)) \\
 52248 &:= ((5! + F(((2+2)!)) - ((F(4)! \times (-8))) \\
 52273 &:= ((F(((5 - F(2)))!)) - ((F(2) + 7!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 52274 &:= ((F(F(((5 \times 2) - 2))) - (7!)) + F(4!)) \\
 52276 &:= ((F(((5 - F(2)))!)) + (2 - 7!)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 52284 &:= (5! - ((F(((2+2)!)/(-8)) - F(4!))) \\
 52343 &:= ((-((5! + F(2))) + (F(3!)!)) - (-((4!)!/(F(F(3!))!))) \\
 52344 &:= (((5+2) + 3!) \times (4! \times F(4))) \\
 52346 &:= ((-((5! - 2)) + (F(3!)!)) - (-((4!)!/(F(F(6))!))) \\
 52360 &:= (-((5! - F(2))) \times ((F(F(3!)) \times (-F(F(6)))) + 0!)) \\
 52366 &:= -(((5! + 2) - (3^{F(6)}) \times F(6))) \\
 52368 &:= -((5! - ((F(2) + F(3))^{F(6)} \times 8))) \\
 52374 &:= ((F(F(F(((5-2)!))) \times (-F(F(3!)))) - (-7 \times (F((F(4)!))!))) \\
 52376 &:= (5! - ((F((-F(2)) + F(F(3!)))) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(6))) \\
 52384 &:= (-((F((5+2)) - (3^8))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 52397 &:= (((F(((5 - F(2)))!)/(-F(3!))) \times (-9)) + F(F(7))) \\
 52413 &:= ((-5) + (2 \times (F(4!) + 1))) - (F(3!)! \\
 52414 &:= -(((F(((5-2)!))! - ((F(4!) - 1) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 52416 &:= (((F(6))! \times (-1)) + (F(4!) \times F(-((2-5))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52416 &:= ((F((5-2)) \times F(4!)) - (F((1 \times 6)))!) \\
 52418 &:= ((F((5-2)) \times (F(4!) + 1)) - 8!) \\
 52421 &:= ((5 - (-2) \times F(4!)) - (F(((2+1)!)))!) \\
 52423 &:= ((5 - ((-2) \times F(4!)) - 2) - (F(3!))!) \\
 52424 &:= -((((F(((5-2)!))! - F((F(4)!)) - (2 \times F(4!)))))) \\
 52425 &:= ((F(F((5+2))) - F((F(4)!)) \times F(F((2+5)))) \\
 52425 &:= ((F(F((5+2))) - F((F(4)!)) \times F(F((2+5)))) \\
 52426 &:= (((-5) - F(24)) \times (-2) - (F(6))!) \\
 52426 &:= -((((F(6)! + ((-2) \times F(4!)) - (2 \times 5)))) \\
 52428 &:= ((((-5) - F(2)) - F(4!)) \times (-2) - 8!) \\
 52432 &:= -((((F(((5-2)!))! + ((F(4!) + F(3!)) \times (-2)))))) \\
 52433 &:= (((F(F((5+2))) - 4)^{F(3)} - F(3!)) \\
 52434 &:= ((F(F((5+2))) - F((4! - F(3)))) \times (-F(4))) \\
 52436 &:= ((52 \times F(F((4+3)))) + (F(6))!) \\
 52437 &:= ((F(F((5+2))) - (F(4)!)) \times (-F(3) + F(F(7)))) \\
 52440 &:= (((F(F((5+2))) - 4)^{F(F(4))} - 0!) \\
 52445 &:= (5 + ((4 - (F(F((F(4)!))²)) \times (-5!))) \\
 52447 &:= ((5! \times (-2) + (F(F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))}))) - F(F(7))) \\
 52448 &:= ((-5) + ((F(2) \times F(4))^{F(F(4)!)})) \times 8) \\
 52462 &:= ((F(((5-2)!))! + (((4)!/(F(F(6)))!) - 2)) \\
 52463 &:= (-((5²)) + ((F(4)^{F(6)}) \times F(3!))) \\
 52464 &:= (F(((5-2)!)) \times ((F(4)^{F(6)}) - F(4))) \\
 52466 &:= (F((5-2)) + (((4)!/(F(F(6)))!) + (F(6)!)) \\
 52468 &:= ((5 - F(2)) + (((4)!/(F(F(6)))!) + 8!)) \\
 52470 &:= (F((5 \times 2)) \times (((F(4)!))! + ((F(F(7)) + 0!)))) \\
 52477 &:= (52 + ((F((F(4)!)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(F(7)))) \\
 52479 &:= (((5 - F(2)))! \times (F(4)⁷) - 9) \\
 52480 &:= (F(((5-2)!)) \times ((F(4)⁸) - 0!)) \\
 52483 &:= (-5) + (((F(2) \times F(4))⁸) \times F(3!)) \\
 52484 &:= ((F(((5-2)!)) \times (F(4)⁸)) - 4) \\
 52494 &:= (((5-2)! + (F((F(4)!)) \times (9⁴))) \\
 52498 &:= ((((((5 - F(2)))!)/(F(F((F(4)!))!))! + ((F(9) + 8!))) \\
 52536 &:= (5! + ((2 \times F(((5 - F(F(3)))!)) - (F(6)!)) \\
 52546 &:= (5! + ((2 \times (5 + F(4!))) - (F(6)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52567 &:= (((5! \times F((2 \times 5))) \times F(6)) - F(F(7))) \\
 52584 &:= ((5 - ((F(2) - 5!) \times F(8))) \times F(F((F(4)!))) \\
 52633 &:= ((52 + F(F(6))) \times (F(F(3)) + 3!)) \\
 52645 &:= (5! + ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) - ((F(F(6))^2))) \times 5)) \\
 52653 &:= (-5!) + ((F((F(2) + F(F(6)))) - 5!) \times 3)) \\
 52664 &:= (((F(F((5 + 2))) \times 6) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(4)!)))! \\
 52667 &:= ((5! \times (-2) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)))) - F(7)) \\
 52674 &:= (-((5!)^2) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 52675 &:= ((-5!) \times F(F(7))) + (((F(6))! \times 2) - (5)) \\
 52675 &:= ((-5) + (2 \times (F(6)!)) - (F(F(7)) \times 5!)) \\
 \\
 52680 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 0 \\
 52681 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 1 \\
 52682 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 2 \\
 52683 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 3 \\
 52684 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 4 \\
 52685 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 5 \\
 52686 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 6 \\
 52687 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 7 \\
 52688 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 8 \\
 52689 &:= 5! \times (-2 + F(F(6)) \times F(8)) + 9 \\
 \\
 52704 &:= (((-((5! + 2)) \times F((F(7) - 0!))) \times (-F(4))) \\
 52730 &:= ((5 \times 2) \times (F(F(7)) + ((3! + 0!)))!)) \\
 52734 &:= (((5 - 2))! + ((F(7)^3) \times 4!)) \\
 52736 &:= (((5 - F(2)))! \times (F(7)^3)) + F(6)) \\
 52746 &:= (-((5! - 2)) \times ((F(7) \times F(F((F(4)!))) - (6!))) \\
 52748 &:= ((52 \times (F(F(7)) + (F(4)!)) + 8!) \\
 52767 &:= (((-((5! + 2)) + F((F(7) + (6)))) \times F(7)) \\
 52773 &:= ((5! - F(((2 + 7) + F(7)))) \times (-3)) \\
 52777 &:= ((5! - F(2)) - ((7 - F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 52794 &:= ((5! \times (-2) + (F(7) \times F(9))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 52795 &:= (-5) + (((-2) + (F(7) \times F(9))) \times 5!) \\
 52795 &:= (-5) + (((F(9) \times F(7)) - 2) \times 5!) \\
 52800 &:= -((5! \times (F(2) - (F(8)^{0!+0!})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 52806 &:= (6 - ((0! - (F(8)^2)) \times 5!)) \\
 52808 &:= (((5! \times F((2 + 8))) + 0!) \times 8) \\
 52824 &:= -(((5! \times (F(2) - (F(8)^2))) - 4!)) \\
 52826 &:= (((F(F(6))^2) - 8) \times (2 + 5!)) \\
 52826 &:= ((5! + 2) \times ((F(8)^2) - F(6))) \\
 52836 &:= (((((5 + 2))! - 8) / F(3)) \times F(F(6))) \\
 52845 &:= (-5) \times (F(((F(4))! + 8) - F(F(F((F(2) + (5))))))) \\
 52845 &:= ((F(F(F(((5 - 2)!))) - F((8 + (F(4)!))) \times 5) \\
 52848 &:= (((-5) + F((-2) + F(8))) \times F(4)) + 8! \\
 52863 &:= ((-F((5^2))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(6))) + (F(3)!)) \\
 52864 &:= (((5! \times F((2 + 8))) + F(6)) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 52865 &:= (((5! \times F(F(6))) \times F(8)) - F((2 \times 5))) \\
 52865 &:= (-F((5 \times 2))) + ((-F(8)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-5!)) \\
 52869 &:= (F(((5 - F(2))!)) + ((F(8) - (6! \times (-9)))) \\
 52877 &:= (((5 - 2) + 8) \times (7! - F(F(7)))) \\
 \\
 52920 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 0 \\
 52921 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 1 \\
 52922 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 2 \\
 52923 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 3 \\
 52924 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 4 \\
 52925 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 5 \\
 52926 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 6 \\
 52927 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 7 \\
 52928 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 8 \\
 52929 &:= 5! \times F(-F(2) + 9)^2 + 9 \\
 \\
 52938 &:= (F(((5 - F(2))!)) + ((9 + (3^8)))) \\
 52944 &:= (((5! \times 2) + F(9)) \times 4!) + F(4!) \\
 52965 &:= (((-5!) - F(F(-(2 - 9)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 52965 &:= (((5! - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F((9 - 2)))) \times (-5)) \\
 52968 &:= (((5! \times F((F(2) + 9))) + F(F(6))) \times 8) \\
 52977 &:= (((5! \times 2) + 9) \times F(F(7))) - (7!) \\
 52978 &:= (((5!^2) \times 9) + (-7) \times F(F(8))) \\
 53013 &:= ((-5!) + F((F(F(3!)) - 0!)) + F(((1 + 3)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 53014 := ((-5!) + F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) + (1 + F(4!))
- 53016 := (-5!) - (3 × (-0! - F((1 + F(F(6))))))
- 53027 := (((5! × F((F(3!) + 0!))) - F(2)) × F(7))
- 53034 := ((-5!) + F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) + ((F(F(3!)) + F(4!)))
- 53040 := ((5! × F((F(3!) + 0!))) × F(((F(4)!) + 0!)))
- 53043 := (((-5) × 3!) + F((0! + F(F((F(4)!)!)))) × 3
- 53044 := ((-F((5 + 3!))) + F((-0! + F(F((F(4)!)!)))) + F(4!))
- 53045 := (5 × ((F(F(F(3!))) - 0!) + ((F((F(4)!)!)/(-5!))))
- 53046 := (((5! × F(F(3!))) + (F(04)!) × F(F(6)))
- 53054 := (((5!/3)^{F(-0!+5)}) - F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))
- 53067 := (((5! × 3) + 0!) × F(F(6))) × 7
- 53083 := ((-5) + F(((3 + 0!)!)) + ((8!/3!))
- 53088 := (((5! × F(F(3!))) + 08) × F(8))
- 53093 := ((5! + (F((F(F(3!)) + 0!) × (-9)))/(-3))
- 53094 := ((-5) + F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) + (-F(9) + F(4!))
- 53124 := ((-5) + F(F((3! + 1))) × F(F((F(2) + (F(4)!)!)))
- 53130 := ((5 - F(3)) × (-1 + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!)))
- 53131 := (-5) - (3 × (-1 - F((F(F(3!)) + 1))))
- 53132 := ((F((5!/3!)) + F(((1 + 3)!) - F(2))
- 53134 := ((F((5!/3!)) + 1) + F((3! × 4)))
- 53139 := (((-5) - F((F(F(3!)) + 1))) × (-3)) - 9
- 53141 := (5 - (3 × (-1 - F((F(F((F(4)!)!)) + 1))))
- 53142 := (((5^{3!}) + F(F(F((F((1 × 4)!)!)))) × 2
- 53143 := ((5 × F(3)) - (F((1 + F(F((F(4)!)!))) × (-3)))
- 53144 := ((5 + F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) + ((F(4!) + (F(4)!)!))
- 53146 := ((5 + F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) + ((F(4!) + F(6)))
- 53147 := (((F((5!/3!)) + 1) + F(4!)) + F(7))
- 53148 := ((-5) - F((F(F(3!)) + 1))) × (4!/(-8))
- 53149 := (-5) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - ((1 + (F(4)!)!)) × 9))
- 53153 := (5 + ((F((F(F(3!)) + 1)) + (5)) × 3))
- 53154 := ((F((5!/3!)) + F(F((1 + 5)))) + F(4!))
- 53157 := ((5! + F(F(3!))) × F(((1⁵) + F(7)))
- 53160 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) × F(6) + 0
- 53161 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) × F(6) + 1

$$53162 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 2$$

$$53163 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 3$$

$$53164 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 4$$

$$53165 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 5$$

$$53166 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 6$$

$$53167 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 7$$

$$53168 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 8$$

$$53169 := (-5! + F(F(F(3!)) - 1)) \times F(6) + 9$$

$$53175 := ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) + 1) - (F(7) \times 5!))$$

$$53178 := (((5! + F(F(3!))) \times F((1 + F(7)))) + (F(8)))$$

$$53184 := ((-(5! - 3) + F((-1 + F(8)))) \times F((F(4)!))$$

$$53208 := (((5! - 3!) - F(20)) \times (-8))$$

$$53223 := (((5 \times 3!) + F(22)) \times 3)$$

$$53234 := ((5 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^3)) - (F(4)!))$$

$$53235 := (-5) - (((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^3) \times (-5))$$

$$53235 := (-5) - (((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^3) \times (-5))$$

$$53240 := (-5) \times (((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)}) \times (-0!))$$

$$53241 := ((5 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) + 1)$$

$$53242 := ((5 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) + 2)$$

$$53243 := (-5) + (F((3! + F(2))) \times (4^{3!}))$$

$$53244 := (5! + ((3 - F((-2) + 4!)) \times (-F(4))))$$

$$53245 := (5 + (((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)}) \times 5))$$

$$53246 := ((5 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) + 6)$$

$$53247 := ((5 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) + 7)$$

$$53249 := ((5 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) + 9)$$

$$53253 := (5! + (3 \times F((25 - 3))))$$

$$53254 := ((F((5!/3!)) + ((F(2) + 5!))) + F(4!))$$

$$53256 := ((-5) + (F(F(3!)) \times (F(2) + 5!))) \times F(F(6))$$

$$53262 := (((5! - 3)^2) - (F(6)!)) \times (-2)$$

$$53272 := -((F((5 + 3!)) - ((-2) + F(F(7)))^2))$$

$$53274 := (5! + ((F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))) + 7) \times F(4)))$$

$$53275 := (-5) - ((3!)! \times (F(2) - 75))$$

$$53276 := ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (2 \times (7 + 6!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53285 &:= ((-5) + ((3!)! \times (-2)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-5))) \\
 53293 &:= (-5) + (F((F(3!) \times 2)) \times (9 \times 3!)) \\
 53295 &:= (-5) \times (F(F(3!)) - (F((2 + 9)) \times 5!)) \\
 53298 &:= ((5! + F(F(3!))) \times ((2 \times 9) \times F(8))) \\
 53302 &:= -((F((-5) + F(F(3!)))) - ((F(F((3! + 0!)))^2))) \\
 53311 &:= (((-5!) + 3!!) - F(F(3))) \times F(11) \\
 53313 &:= (((5!/F(3)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1))) \times 3) \\
 53316 &:= (((5! - 3!)^{F(3)}) + (F((1 \times 6)))!) \\
 53328 &:= (((-5!) + F(F(3!))) + F((F(F(3!)) - F(2)))) \times 8) \\
 53332 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (3! \times F(F((3! + F(2))))) \\
 53336 &:= (((F((5!/3!)) - F(3!)) \times F(3!)) - (6!)) \\
 53337 &:= ((-5) \times (-F(F(3)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (-3!) \times F(F(7))) \\
 53347 &:= (-5) + ((F(3!) + (F(3!)^4)) \times F(7)) \\
 53355 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F((F(3) \times 5)) \times 5))) \\
 53356 &:= (-5) + (F(F(3!)) \times ((F(F(3)) + 5!) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 53357 &:= (((5! \times F(3)) - 3!) - (5)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 53360 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(F(6)) - 0!) \\
 53361 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(F((6 \times 1))) \\
 53362 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(F(6)) + F(2)) \\
 53363 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(F(6)) + F(3)) \\
 53364 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(F(6)) + F(4)) \\
 53365 &:= (((-5) - F(3!)) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(6))) \times 5) \\
 53367 &:= (((5! - (F(3!)!)) \times F(3!)) / (-6) - F(F(7))) \\
 53368 &:= (((F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times (F(3!)!)) / 6!) + 8!) \\
 53370 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(F(3!)) \times F(7)) - 0!)) \\
 53372 &:= ((5 + 3!) + ((-F(3)) + F(F(7)))^2) \\
 53373 &:= (5 + (((F(3!)! / (3!)!) \times (F(F(7)) + 3!))) \\
 53374 &:= (((F((5!/3!)) + F(3!)) + F(F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 53375 &:= ((-5!) \times F(F(3!))) - ((F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) \times (-5)) \\
 53377 &:= ((-((5! - 3!)) \times F(3!)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 53378 &:= ((5! \times (-((3!)! - F(F(3!)))) - (-F(7) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 53379 &:= (((5^{F(3)}) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (7!)) \times 9) \\
 53384 &:= (((5^{F(3)}) / 3!) + F(F(8))) \times 4) \\
 53385 &:= (-5) \times (3 - (F((3 + 8)) \times 5!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$53386 := ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(3!) \times (F(8) \times F(6))))$$

$$53387 := (((-5!) + 3!!) \times F((3 + 8))) - F(7)$$

$$53394 := (((-5!) + 3!!) \times F((F(3) + 9))) - (F(4))!$$

$$53395 := (((-5!) + 3!!) \times F((F(3) + 9))) - (5)$$

$$53396 := (((5^{3!}) \times 3!) - F(9)) - (F(6))!$$

$$53398 := ((-5!) + (3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 9!)))/F(8)$$

$$53403 := (((5! \times F(F(3!))) + (4! - 0!)) \times F(F(3!)))$$

$$53405 := (((5! \times F((F(3!) + F(4)))) + 0!) \times 5)$$

$$53408 := ((-F((5 + 3!))) + F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!))) \times 8$$

$$53410 := ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((4! \times F(10))))$$

$$53416 := ((-5) + (3!^{F(4)!})) + F((-1 + F(F(6))))$$

$$53419 := (((5!^{F(3)}) \times 4) - F(19))$$

$$53421 := (F((5!/3!)) + ((F(4))!^{(2+1)!}))$$

$$53423 := (((5! - 3!) \times ((F(4))!)) - (F(23)))$$

$$53425 := (((-5!) \times (3!)!)/4 + F(25))$$

$$53426 := ((5 + (3!^{F(4)!})) + F((-F(2) + F(F(6))))$$

$$53428 := (((5^{3!}) \times (F(4))!) - (2 + 8!))$$

$$53430 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 0$$

$$53431 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 1$$

$$53432 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 2$$

$$53433 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 3$$

$$53434 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 4$$

$$53435 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 5$$

$$53436 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 6$$

$$53437 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 7$$

$$53438 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 8$$

$$53439 := 5^{3!} \times F(4)! - F(3)! + 9$$

$$53442 := (((5 + 3)!) - ((F(4))^{F(F(4)!))} \times (-2)))$$

$$53444 := (((5! + (3^{F(F(4)!)})) \times F((F(4))!)) - 4)$$

$$53445 := (((5! + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(((F(4))! + F((F(4))!)))) \times 5)$$

$$53447 := ((5 + (F(3))!) + ((F(4))! \times (F(4))^7))$$

$$53450 := (-5) \times ((F(3))^{F(F(4)!)} - F(F(F((5 + 0!))))$$

$$53453 := (5 + (((3^{F(F(4)!)} + 5!) \times F(3!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53458 &:= ((-53) \times 4!) - (-5) \times F(F(8))) \\
 53460 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(F(3!))) - F(F((F(4)!))) - (F(F((F(6) - 0!)))))) \\
 53463 &:= (((F((5 + F(3)))^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(3)!)) \\
 53464 &:= (((5! + F(3)) + (F(4)^{F(6)})) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 53466 &:= (((-(5^{3!}) - (F(4)!)) \times (-6)) - (F(6)!)) \\
 53470 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (F(7) - 0!)))) \\
 53472 &:= (5! + ((F(F(3!)) + ((F(4)!))!) \times 72)) \\
 53473 &:= (((-5!) - 3!!) + (4!)) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)}) \\
 53474 &:= (5! + ((F(F(3)) + ((F(4)!))!) \times 74)) \\
 53475 &:= (((-5) + 3!!) - F(F(4))) \times 75 \\
 53476 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((-4!) + F(F(7))) \times 6)) \\
 53477 &:= (5! + (((3!^{F(4)} + F(7)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 53479 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (4! + F(F(7)))) + F(9)) \\
 53482 &:= ((5! + F(F(3))) \times (F(F(F(4))) + ((F(8)^2))) \\
 53484 &:= (((5! - 3) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(8)))))) \times F(4) \\
 53487 &:= (((5! - (F(3)!))!)/(-F(4))) + (8! - F(F(7))) \\
 53489 &:= (((-5!) + 3!!) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 89 \\
 53493 &:= ((5! + F((F((3 + 4) + 9))) \times 3) \\
 53524 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (5! \times (-2)))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 53525 &:= (((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! + F(2))) \times 5) \\
 \\
 53530 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 0 \\
 53531 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 1 \\
 53532 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 2 \\
 53533 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 3 \\
 53534 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 4 \\
 53535 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 5 \\
 53536 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 6 \\
 53537 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 7 \\
 53538 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 8 \\
 53539 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5! \times F(3)) + 9 \\
 \\
 53540 &:= (5 \times ((F(F(F(3!))) - (5)) - F(F(((F(4)! + 0!)))))) \\
 53544 &:= (((5!/F(3)) \times 5!) + F(4!)) - (4!) \\
 53545 &:= (((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (5! - F(4))) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$53547 := ((5! \times (3!)!) - ((5! + F(F((F(4))!))) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$53549 := ((-5) \times ((3^5 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) + F(9))$$

$$53554 := ((((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 5!) \times 5) + 4!$$

$$53555 := (((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (5 - 5!)) \times 5$$

$$53560 := (-5) \times ((F(F((F(3) + (5)))) - F(F(F(6)))) + 0!))$$

$$53564 := ((-5) - 3!) + (F((5 + F(6)))^{F(F(4))})$$

$$53566 := (((((5 + 3)!/5) \times F(6)) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$53570 := (5 \times ((F(F((3 + 5))) - F(F(7))) + 0!))$$

$$53573 := ((5 \times (F(F((3 + 5))) - F(F(7)))) + F(3!))$$

$$53574 := ((5 - (3! \times 5!)) + (F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$53576 := ((5 + 3!) + (-5) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6))))))$$

$$53577 := ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (5 - F(F(7)))) - F(7))$$

$$53599 := (((5 + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5) - (F(9) \times F(9)))$$

$$53608 := (((5! - (F(3!)!)/(-6)) + 0!) \times 8)$$

$$53624 := ((F((5!/3!)) - 62) \times F((F(4))!))$$

$$53627 := ((5! \times (3! + (F(F(6))^2))) - F(7))$$

$$53632 := ((5! \times (3!)!) - ((F(6)^{3+2}))$$

$$53633 := ((F((5 + F(3))) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) - ((3!)!))$$

$$53634 := (-5!) + (((F(3!) \times (F(6)!)/3!) - (F(4))!))$$

$$53635 := (-5!) - (((F(3!) \times (F(6)!)/(-3!)) + (5)))$$

$$53635 := (-5!) - (((F(3!) \times (F(6)!)/(-3!)) + (5)))$$

$$53636 := (-5!) + (((-3) + (F(6)!)) \times F(3!)/6)$$

$$53637 := ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (6^3))) - F(7))$$

$$53638 := (-5!) + (((3! - (F(6)!)/(-3)) + 8!))$$

$$53640 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 0$$

$$53641 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 1$$

$$53642 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 2$$

$$53643 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 3$$

$$53644 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 4$$

$$53645 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 5$$

$$53646 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 6$$

$$53647 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 7$$

$$53648 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 8$$

$$53649 := (-5! + F(3!) \times F(6)!)/F(4)! + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53650 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (6^{F(5-0!)}))) \\
 53653 &:= (((5! \times (3!)!) - (F(6)^5)) + F(F(3!))) \\
 53654 &:= (((-5) \times F((3 \times 6))) \times (-5) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\
 53657 &:= ((-5!) - 3!!) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-5) + F(F(7)))) \\
 53664 &:= (((5! - 3!) \times F(6)) \times F(6) + F(4!)) \\
 53665 &:= ((-5!) \times F(3!)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 53666 &:= (((5!^{F(3)})/6) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6)!) \\
 53667 &:= (F((5 + 3!)) \times (F((F(F(6)) - 6) - 7)) \\
 53668 &:= ((F((5 + 3!)) \times (6! + (6))) - F(F(8))) \\
 \\
 53670 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 0 \\
 53671 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 1 \\
 53672 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 2 \\
 53673 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 3 \\
 53674 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 4 \\
 53675 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 5 \\
 53676 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 6 \\
 53677 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 7 \\
 53678 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 8 \\
 53679 &:= 5 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + 9 \\
 \\
 53684 &:= (((-5) \times (3! + 6!)) + F(F(8))) + F(4!) \\
 53685 &:= (((-5!) - F((3 + F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \times 5 \\
 53687 &:= ((((-5!) - (F(3!)!)/6) \times (-8) - F(F(7))) \\
 53693 &:= (5 + (((F(3!)!)/(-6) + 9) \times (-F(3!))) \\
 53694 &:= -(((F((5!/3!)) + F(F(6))) - (9!/(F(4)!))) \\
 53697 &:= (((5! \times (F(3)^6) - 9) \times 7) \\
 53702 &:= (-((5! + F(3))) + ((F(F(7)) - 0!)^2)) \\
 53703 &:= ((-5!) - F(F(3))) + ((F(F(7)) - 0!)^{F(3)}) \\
 53704 &:= (-5!) + (((-F(3)) + F(F(7))) + 0!)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 53712 &:= (((5! \times 3) + F(7)) \times F(12)) \\
 53714 &:= (((-5) \times (3!)!) + F(F((7 + 1)))) + F(4!) \\
 53725 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F(F(7)) - (2^5)))) \\
 53726 &:= (((5! \times ((3!)! - 7))/2) + F(F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53728 &:= ((F((5!/3!)) - (7^2)) \times 8) \\
 53733 &:= (((5!^{F(3)}) - F((F(7) + 3))) + (F(3)!)) \\
 53735 &:= ((-5!) \times F(3!)) - ((-7) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-5)) \\
 53735 &:= ((-5!) \times F(3!)) - ((-7) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-5)) \\
 53736 &:= ((((-5!) \times F(3!)) \times (-7)) - 3) \times F(6) \\
 53744 &:= ((((-5!) \times F(3!)) \times (-7)) - F(F(4))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 53747 &:= ((((-5!) \times F(3!)) \times (-7)) \times F((F(4)!)) - F(7)) \\
 53748 &:= ((5^{3!}) - ((F(7)^{F(4)}) - 8!)) \\
 53755 &:= (((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (75)) \times 5) \\
 53756 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (-F(7) + F((-5) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 53759 &:= (5 + ((F(F(3!)) + (F(7) \times 5!)) \times F(9))) \\
 \\
 53760 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 0 \\
 53761 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 1 \\
 53762 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 2 \\
 53763 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 3 \\
 53764 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 4 \\
 53765 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 5 \\
 53766 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 6 \\
 53767 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 7 \\
 53768 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 8 \\
 53769 &:= 5! \times F(3!) \times 7 \times F(6) + 9 \\
 \\
 53774 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(7)))) + (F(F(7)) - (4!))) \\
 53775 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F(F(7)) - (7!/5!)))) \\
 53777 &:= ((5!^{F(3)}) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(7) \times F(7)))) \\
 53784 &:= (((-5!) \times F(3!)) \times (-7 \times 8)) + (4!) \\
 53786 &:= (((5! \times (3 \times 7)) + F(F(8))) + (F(6)!)) \\
 53789 &:= ((((-5) - 3!) \times F(F(7))) \times (-F(8))) - F(9) \\
 53794 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F(7) \times 9) \times F((F(4)!)))) \\
 53798 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(7)))) + (F((F(9) - F(8)))))) \\
 53802 &:= ((5! + F(3)) \times (F(8)^02)) \\
 53818 &:= (-5) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(8) - F(18)))) \\
 53822 &:= (((5! \times F(3)) - 8^2) - 2) \\
 53823 &:= (((5! \times F(3)) - 8^2) - F(F(3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53824 &:= (((5! \times F(3)) - 8)^{-2+4}) \\
 53832 &:= (-5! + (F(3!) \times (-F(8)) + F((F(F(3!)) - F(2)))))) \\
 53834 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (-8!)/(F(F(3!)) + (4!))) \\
 53837 &:= (((5! \times F(3)) - 8)^{F(3)} + F(7)) \\
 53843 &:= ((((-5!) \times F(F(3!))) - F(F(8))) \times (-4)) - F(F(3!))) \\
 53844 &:= ((F((5 + 3)) + (8!/F(4))) \times 4) \\
 53845 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F((8 + F(4)))) \times 5) \\
 53846 &:= ((F((5 + 3!)) \times (8 + ((F(4)!))!) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 53847 &:= (((5 - F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) \times (-F((F(4)!))!) - F(F(7))) \\
 53848 &:= (((5 + 3!) + (8!/(F(4)!))!) \times 8) \\
 53849 &:= (((-5) + (F(3)!))! - F(F(8))) - (((F(4)!))! \times (-F(9))) \\
 53853 &:= (((5! + F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))))) + 5!) \times 3) \\
 53855 &:= (((F((5 \times F(3))) - F(F(8))) + 5!) \times (-5)) \\
 53857 &:= (F(((5 \times 3) + 8)) - (-5 \times 7!)) \\
 53864 &:= (((5 - F(F(3))) \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6)!)/4)) \\
 53865 &:= (((-5) + (F(3!) \times (-F(8)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 53867 &:= (5! - ((F(3!) \times (8!/(-6))) + F(7))) \\
 53873 &:= (((-5!) \times F(F(3!))) \times (-F(8))) + ((F(F(7)) + 3!)) \\
 53874 &:= ((5 - ((-F(3)) \times F(F(8))) - (7!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 53875 &:= ((-5) \times (3 - F(F(8)))) - (7 \times 5!) \\
 53878 &:= ((5!^{F(3)}) - ((F(F(8))/F(7)) - 8!)) \\
 53879 &:= ((5 + 3!!) + ((F(F(8)) - (7!)) \times 9)) \\
 \\
 53880 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 0 \\
 53881 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 1 \\
 53882 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 2 \\
 53883 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 3 \\
 53884 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 4 \\
 53885 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 5 \\
 53886 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 6 \\
 53887 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 7 \\
 53888 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 8 \\
 53889 &:= 5! \times (F(3!) + F(8) \times F(8)) + 9 \\
 \\
 53890 &:= (-5) \times ((F(3!) \times F(8)) - F(F((9 - 0!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 53893 := ((F((5 + F(F(3!)))) + ((8! - F(9))))/3)
- 53894 := (((5! × 3) × F(8) - F(9)) + F(4!))
- 53896 := ((-5) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8)))) - (9 + 6!))
- 53905 := (5 × (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(9) - 0!) × 5)))
- 53914 := ((5 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(9) × ((1 × 4)!))
- 53924 := (((5! + F(3)) × F(9)) × F((F(2) + (F(4)!))))
- 53928 := (((-5) + F(F(3!))) - F((9 × 2))) × (-F(8)))
- 53929 := ((5 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (9 × F((2 + 9))))
- 53934 := ((((-5!) - 3!) × (-9)) + 3!) + F(4!))
- 53935 := (((-(5³)) - F(9)) + F(F(F(3!)))) × 5
- 53935 := (((-(5³)) - F(9)) + F(F(F(3!)))) × 5
- 53937 := (((5! + F(3)) × F(9)) + F(F(3))) × F(7))
- 53943 := (5! - ((F(F(3!)) - F((9 × F(F(4)))))) × F(F(3!)))
- 53944 := (((5 - F(F(3)))⁹ - F(4!))/4)
- 53945 := (((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(9) + F(4))) × 5
- 53946 := (((5!/3) + F(9)) × (F(4)⁶))
- 53947 := ((5 × (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9))) - (((F(4)! + F(F(7))))))
- 53948 := (((5! - F(F(3!))) × (-F(9))) + ((F(4!) + F(F(8))))))
- 53954 := (((5! - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(9)) × (-5)) - (F(4)!)
- 53955 := (((5! - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(9)) × (-5)) - (5))
- 53956 := ((5 × F(F(F(3!)))) - ((9 + 5!) × 6))
- 53960 := (((5! - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(9)) × (-6 + 0!))
- 53963 := ((5 × (F(F(F(3!))) - 9)) - (6! + F(3)))
- 53964 := ((5 × (F(F(F(3!))) - 9)) - (6! + F(F(F(4))))))
- 53965 := ((((-5!) + F(F(3))) - F(9)) + F(F(F(6)))) × 5
- 53966 := (((5!^{F(3)}) - F(9)) - 6!) + (F(6)!)
- 53968 := (((-5!) × (F(F(3)) + F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))) × 8
- 53973 := (5! + ((3 × F((9 + F(7)))) + 3!))
- 53976 := ((5 + F(F(3!))) × ((9 × F(F(7))) - F(F(6))))
- 53982 := ((5 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(9) × (F(8) + F(2))))
- 53983 := ((5 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (9 × 83))
- 53984 := ((F((5!/3!)) - (9 + 8)) × F((F(4)!))
- 53986 := ((5 × (F(F(F(3!))) - 9)) + ((F(8) - 6!)))
- 53997 := (-5!) + (F(F(3!)) × (F((9 + 9)) - (7)))
- 54004 := ((5 × (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 0!)) - (0! + ((F(4)!)!))

$$\begin{aligned}
 54005 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 0!)) - (((0! + (5))))!) \\
 54006 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 0!)) + (0! - 6!)) \\
 54008 &:= (-(5!) - (F((F(4)!)) \times (-(0!) - F(-((0! - F(8))))))) \\
 54010 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (((((0! + 1) + 0!))!))!) \\
 54014 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0!)) - (1 + ((F(4)!))!)) \\
 54015 &:= (((-5) \times ((F(4)!))! - 0!) \times (-15)) \\
 54016 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0!)) + (1 - 6!)) \\
 54024 &:= (-(5! - (4!^{0!+2})) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 54025 &:= (((5! + F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(F(F(((0! + 2)!)))) \times (-5)) \\
 54034 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (((03)! - (4!))) \\
 54036 &:= (((F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) + 0!)^{F(3)} - (6!)) \\
 54039 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 0!)) - ((3!) - F(9))) \\
 54044 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((F((0! + F((F(4)!)) - (((F(4)!))!)))) \\
 54048 &:= (((F((5 \times 4)) - 0!) - F((F(4)!)) \times 8) \\
 54049 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0!)) - (((F(4)!))! - F(9))) \\
 54056 &:= ((-F((5 \times 4)) + F((0! + (5)))) \times (-F(6))) \\
 54064 &:= (((F((5 \times 4)) - 0!) - (6)) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 54065 &:= (((-5!) - F(((F(4)! + 0!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 54066 &:= (-(54) + (F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times F(6)) \\
 54067 &:= (((F((-5) + 4!)) - 0!) - F(F(6)) \times F(7)) \\
 54075 &:= (((5! \times (F(4)!)) + 0!) \times 75) \\
 54076 &:= ((5! + (F(4!) \times (0 - 7)))/(-6)) \\
 54077 &:= (F((5 + F(4))) + ((-0!) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 \\
 54080 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 0 \\
 54081 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 1 \\
 54082 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 2 \\
 54083 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 3 \\
 54084 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 4 \\
 54085 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 5 \\
 54086 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 6 \\
 54087 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 7 \\
 54088 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 8 \\
 54089 &:= (-5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \times 8 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$54090 := (((-5!) + ((F(4))!) + 0!) \times 90)$$

$$54104 := (((F((5 \times 4)) - 1) - 0!) \times F((F(4))!))$$

$$54112 := ((F((5 \times 4)) - 1) \times F(((1 + 2)!))$$

$$54115 := (-5) + (F((F(4))!) \times F((-1 + F(F((1 + 5))))))$$

$$54120 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 0$$

$$54121 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 1$$

$$54122 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 2$$

$$54123 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 3$$

$$54124 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 4$$

$$54125 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 5$$

$$54126 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 6$$

$$54127 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 7$$

$$54128 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 8$$

$$54129 := F(5 \times 4) \times F((1 + 2)!) + 9$$

$$54130 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 0$$

$$54131 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 1$$

$$54132 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 2$$

$$54133 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 3$$

$$54134 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 4$$

$$54135 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5$$

$$54136 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 6$$

$$54137 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 7$$

$$54138 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 8$$

$$54139 := 5 \times (-(4 + 1)! + F(F(F(3!)))) + 9$$

$$54143 := (((5 + F(4))!) - (1 - (4^3)))$$

$$54144 := (((5 + 4) - 1)!) + (4!^{F(4)})$$

$$54145 := (((-5!) + F(F(F((4 - 1)!)))) + F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54145 := (((-5!) + F(F(F((4 - 1)!)))) + F(4)) \times 5$$

$$54146 := (((5! \times F(4)) \times ((1 + 4)!) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$54147 := (((-5) - F((F(F((F(4))!) - 1))) \times (-F((F(4))!))) - F(7))$$

$$54148 := (-5!) + ((F(F((F(4))! + 1)))^{F(F(4))} - (F(8)))$$

$$54149 := (-5) + ((F((F(4))!) \times F((-1 + F(F((F(4))!)))) + F(9))$$

- 54154 := (((5! - F(F(F(((4 - 1)!)))))) × (-5)) + 4!)
 54155 := (((5! - F(F(F(((4 - 1)!)))))) - (5)) × (-5))
 54156 := ((((-5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + 1) × 5) + (F(F(6)))
 54159 := (((5! - F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + 1) × (-5)) + F(9)
- 54160 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 0
 54161 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 1
 54162 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 2
 54163 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 3
 54164 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 4
 54165 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 5
 54166 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 6
 54167 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 7
 54168 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 8
 54169 := (5 + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) × F(6) + 9
- 54170 := (-5!) - ((F(F(((F(4)! + 1))) × (-F(F(7)))) - 0!))
 54172 := (-((5! - F(4))) + (F(F((1 × 7)))²))
 54173 := (-((5! - (4))) + (F(F((1 × 7)))^{F(3)}))
 54174 := ((5 - ((4 + 1)!)) + (F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}))
 54177 := ((-5!) + F(((4 - 1)!)) + (F(F(7)) × F(F(7))))
 54179 := ((-5!) + F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(17) × F(9)))
 54184 := ((F((5 × 4)) + (1 × 8)) × F((F(4)!))
 54186 := (-5!) + ((F(F(4)) + F(18)) × F(F(6)))
 54194 := ((5! - 41) × (-F(9)) + ((F(4)!))!)
 54205 := (((-5) × F(F((F(4)!))) + F(F(F(((2 + 0)!)))))) × 5)
 54208 := (5! + ((-4) + F(20)) × 8)
 54218 := ((5 × F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (2¹⁺⁸))
 54224 := (5! + ((F((F(F((F(4)!)) - F(2))) - 2) × F((F(4)!))))
 54226 := ((5 × F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (((2 + 2)! × F(F(6))))
 54230 := (F((5 × F(F(4)))) × (F((2 × F(3!)) - 0!))
 54232 := (5! + (F((F(4)!)) × (-F(2) + F((F(F(3!)) - F(2))))))
 54233 := ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))))² - ((F(3!))! / (3!))
 54234 := -((F((5 × F(F(4)))) - (F(F((F(2) + 3!)))^{F(F(4))}))
 54235 := (((-5!) + F(F((4 × 2)))) + F(F(3!))) × 5

$$\begin{aligned}
 54236 &:= (((-5!) - F(4!)) \times (F(2) + 3!)) / (-6) \\
 54237 &:= (((5! - F(F(4)))^2) + (F(3!))!) - 7 \\
 54238 &:= (((5! - F(F(4)))^2) - (3! - 8!)) \\
 \\
 54240 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 \\
 54241 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 \\
 54242 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 \\
 54243 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 \\
 54244 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 \\
 54245 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 \\
 54246 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 \\
 54247 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 \\
 54248 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 8 \\
 54249 &:= 5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 9 \\
 \\
 54254 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((F(2) - 5!) \times (-4))) \\
 54255 &:= (((-5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 25) \times 5) \\
 54256 &:= (5! + (F((F(4)!)) \times (2 + F((5!/6)))))) \\
 54257 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((2 \times 5!) + F(F(7)))) \\
 54259 &:= (-5) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times F((F(-((2 - 5))) \times 9)))) \\
 54265 &:= ((5! + F(4!)) + ((F(2) + (6^5)))) \\
 54266 &:= (((5! \times (4! + F(2))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6)!)) \\
 54269 &:= (5 + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(((F(2) + F(6)) + 9)))) \\
 54279 &:= (((5! + 4!) \times F((2 \times 7))) - 9) \\
 54280 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))))^2) - (8 + 0!) \\
 54283 &:= (-5) + (F((4!/2)) \times F((8 + 3!))) \\
 54285 &:= ((5 + (F(4)!)) \times (F((2 \times 8)) \times 5)) \\
 54302 &:= (F((5 + F(F(4)))) + (F(F((3! + 0!)))^2)) \\
 54303 &:= (5 + (F((-4) + F(F(3!))) \times F((0! + F(3!)))) \\
 54304 &:= ((5 \times F(4)) + (F(F((3! + 0!)))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 54313 &:= (((5 - F(F(F(4))))!) + ((F(F((3! + 1)))^{F(3)})) \\
 54314 &:= ((F((-5) + 4!) - 3) \times F((1 + (F(4)!))) \\
 54315 &:= (((5 \times ((F(4)!))!) + F(F(3!))) \times 15) \\
 54318 &:= (54 - (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(18)))) \\
 54319 &:= ((F((-5) + 4!) \times F((3! + 1))) - F(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54323 &:= (F((5+4)) + (F(F((3! + F(2))))^{F(3)})) \\
 54325 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (3^{-F(2)+5})) \\
 54326 &:= (((5! \times (-F(4) - 3!)) / (-2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 54327 &:= ((F((-5) + 4!)) - F(3)) \times (F(2) \times F(7)) \\
 54328 &:= (((5 + F(F((F(4)!))) + F((F(F(3!)) - F(2)))) \times 8) \\
 54330 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((3!)/(F(3!) + 0!))) \\
 54333 &:= ((-5) \times (4 - F(F(F(3!)))) - F((3! + F(3!)))) \\
 54334 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^{F(3)} + (F(F(3!)) + (4!))) \\
 54335 &:= (((5 - (4 \times F(F(3!)))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5) \\
 54337 &:= (((F((5 \times 4)) - F(3)) \times F(3!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 54338 &:= ((-5) \times (F(4) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (F((3! + 8)))) \\
 54339 &:= (-5!) + (((F(4!) + 3) - (F(3!)!) \times 9)) \\
 54340 &:= (F((5 \times F(F(4)))) \times (F((F(3)^4) + 0!)) \\
 54342 &:= (5! + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (F((3! \times F(4)) - 2))) \\
 54344 &:= (((5 \times 4)^3 - 4!) + F(4!)) \\
 54345 &:= (((-5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (3 \times 4!)) \times 5) \\
 54345 &:= (((-5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (3 \times 4!)) \times 5) \\
 54346 &:= (((-((5! - 4!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 54347 &:= (((F((5 \times 4)) \times F(3!)) - (F(4)!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 54352 &:= ((F((-5) + 4!) \times F((F(3) + (5)))) - F(2)) \\
 54353 &:= (F((-5) + 4!) \times ((F(3) + (5)) + 3!)) \\
 54354 &:= ((F((-5) + 4!) \times F((F(3) + (5)))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 54355 &:= ((-5) + (F((F(4)!))!) + ((-3) + 5!) \times 5!) \\
 54356 &:= (((5! - 4) \times (F(F(3)) + 5!)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 54357 &:= (-5!) + (((-4) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5) - F(F(7))) \\
 54358 &:= (((5! + 4) \times (-3)) - (-5) \times F(F(8))) \\
 54359 &:= -(((5^{F(4)!}) - ((3!^5) \times 9)) \\
 54360 &:= ((5! \times F(F(4))) + (F(3!) \times F((F(F(6)) - 0!))) \\
 54362 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F(3!) - (6!/(-2)))) \\
 54363 &:= (((5 + F((4! - 3!))) \times F(F(6))) - 3!) \\
 54364 &:= (((-5!) + F(4!)) / 3!) + (6^{F(4)!}) \\
 54365 &:= (-5) + (((4! \times (-3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 54366 &:= ((F((-5) + 4!) + F(F(3))) \times (F(F(6)) - F(6))) \\
 54367 &:= ((-5) \times ((4! + F(3)) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$54368 := ((-5) \times (-F(4) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (F((6 + 8))))$$

$$54369 := (((-5) + F(4!)) - F(3)) - (F(6)!) \times 9$$

$$54370 := (-5) \times ((4! \times 3) - F(F((7 + 0!))))$$

$$54372 := (F((5 + (F(4)!)) - (3! - (F(F(7))^2)))$$

$$54373 := (((F((-5) + 4!)) + F(3)) \times F(7)) - 3!$$

$$54374 := (((F((-5) + 4!)) + F(F(3))) \times F(7)) + F((F(4)!))$$

$$54375 := ((5 + ((F(4) \times F(3)))!) \times 75)$$

$$54377 := ((-5) \times (4! - F((3 \times 7)))) - F(F(7))$$

$$54379 := ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((3 \times F(7)) \times 9))$$

$$54382 := (5! + ((F((4! - 3!)) \times F(8)) - 2))$$

$$54383 := (5! + ((F((4! - 3!)) \times F(8)) - F(F(3))))$$

$$54384 := (((5^{F(4)!}) - (3^8)) \times (F(4)!))$$

$$54386 := (((5! \times (4! + F(3))) + F(F(8))) + (F(6)!))$$

$$54387 := ((-5) \times ((4! - F(3)) - F(F(8)))) - F(F(7))$$

$$54388 := ((5! + (4)) - (F((-3) + F(8))) \times (-F(8)))$$

$$54390 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 0$$

$$54391 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 1$$

$$54392 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 2$$

$$54393 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 3$$

$$54394 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 4$$

$$54395 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 5$$

$$54396 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 6$$

$$54397 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 7$$

$$54398 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 8$$

$$54399 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F(3) \times F(9)) + 9$$

$$54403 := ((5! - (F(4)!)) + (F(F(((F(4)! + 0!))))^{F(3)}))$$

$$54405 := (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F(((F(4)! + 0!)) \times 5)))$$

$$54407 := ((5! - F(F(4))) - (F(F(((F(4)! + 0!))) \times (-F(F(7))))))$$

$$54408 := (5! + (F((F(4)!)) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) + (F(-((0! - F(8))))))))$$

$$54410 := (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F((F(4)!))^{1+0!})))$$

$$54412 := ((5! + F(4)) + (F(F(((F(4)! + 1)))^2))$$

$$54413 := ((5! + (4)) + (F(F(((F(4)! + 1)))^{F(3)}))$$

$$54414 := ((5^{F(4)} + (F(F(((F(4)! + 1)))^{F(F(4))})))$$

- 54415 := $(-(5) \times ((F(4) \times F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(F(F((1+5)))))))$
- 54417 := $((5! + F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(((F(4))! + 1))) \times (-F(F(7))))))$
- 54418 := $((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (4! \times F(-((1-8)))))$
- 54423 := $((5+4) \times ((F(4!) - F(2)) - (F(3))!))$
- 54425 := $((((-5!)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - F(2)) \times 5$
- 54426 := $(5! + ((F((F(4) \times (F(4))!)) + 2) \times F(F(6))))$
- 54427 := $(-5) + (((F(4))!^{F(4)+2}) \times 7)$
- 54430 := $((5!/F(F(4))) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-3! - 0!))$
- 54431 := $((F((-5) + 4!)) + (F(4))! \times F((3! + 1)))$
- 54432 := $((5! + (F(4))!) \times 432)$
- 54433 := $((5! + 4!) + (F(F((4+3)))^{F(3)}))$
- 54434 := $((-(5! \times 4!) + F(4!)) + F((-3) + 4!))$
- 54435 := $(((-5) \times (-F(4) - F(4!))) + (F(3))!)/5$
- 54436 := $((-((5! \times 4!)) + F(4!)) + F(3) + F(F(F(6))))$
- 54437 := $((-5!) + F(4!)) - ((F(4) - (F(3))^{F(7)}))$
- 54438 := $(((-5!) \times ((F(4))!)/(-4)) + (3 \times F(F(8))))$
- 54439 := $((5 + F(F(4))) - ((-F(4!)) + (F(3))! \times 9))$
- 54440 := $((-5!) + F(4!)) + (F(F(4))^{F(F(4)!+0!))}$
- 54441 := $((5+4) \times ((F(4!) - (F((F(4))!))! + 1))$
- 54442 := $((5 - (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-((F(4))!^4)))) \times 2$
- 54444 := $((((-5) \times (F((F(4))!))! - 4!)/(-F(F(4)))) - F(4!))$
- 54445 := $((F((5 + F(F(4)))) + F(4!)) + ((F((F(4))!))!)/5)$
- 54445 := $((F((5 + F(F(4)))) + F(4!)) + ((F((F(4))!))!)/5)$
- 54446 := $(-5!) + (((4^{F(F(4)!)} - 4!) - F(F(F(6))))$
- 54447 := $((5!^{F(F(4))}) + (F((F(4))!))! - (F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(7)))$
- 54449 := $((-5) \times ((F(4) \times F(F((F(4))!))) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + F(9))$
- 54450 := $((5! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 450)$
- 54453 := $((5 + F(F(4))) \times (((F(4))!^5) + 3))$
- 54454 := $((((-5!)/F(F(4))) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-5) + 4!)$
- 54456 := $((5! - (F(4))!) \times (4 + 5!)) + (F(6))!$
- 54457 := $((5 + F(4)) + F((4! - 5))) \times F(7)$
- 54458 := $((-F((5+4))) \times F((F(4))!)) - (-5 \times F(F(8)))$
- 54460 := $(-5) \times ((F((4 + (F(4))!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - 0!)$
- 54463 := $((-5) + F(4!)) + (((F(4))!)/F(6))^{F(3)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54464 &:= (- (5!) + (((4^{F(F(4)!)}) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 54465 &:= ((((- (5) - 4!) - 4!) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 54466 &:= (- (((5! + (4)) - (4^{F(6)}))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 54467 &:= ((5 - (((F(4))!^{F(4)!}) / (-6))) \times 7) \\
 54468 &:= (((- (5!) - F(F(4))) + (4^{F(6)})) - F(F(8))) \\
 54469 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((F((F(4)!)) + (F(F(6)))) \times 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54470 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 0 \\
 54471 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 1 \\
 54472 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 2 \\
 54473 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 3 \\
 54474 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 4 \\
 54475 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 5 \\
 54476 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 6 \\
 54477 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 7 \\
 54478 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 8 \\
 54479 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 4 \times F(7)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54480 &:= (((5! - F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + ((8! - 0!)) \\
 54481 &:= (((5! - F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + ((8 \times 1)!)) \\
 54482 &:= (((5! - F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + ((8! + F(2)))) \\
 54483 &:= (((5! - F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + ((8! + F(3)))) \\
 54484 &:= ((- (5) \times ((4! + 4!) - F(F(8)))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 54486 &:= ((5 + 4) \times (F(4!) - ((8! - (6)))) \\
 54487 &:= (((5 \times 4!)^{F(F(4))}) + 8!) - F(F(7)) \\
 54489 &:= ((- (5) \times (F((4 + (F(4)!)) - F(F(8)))) + F(9)) \\
 54490 &:= (- (5) \times ((4! + 4!) - F(F((9 - 0!)))) \\
 54492 &:= ((- (5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - (F(F((9 - 2)))) \\
 54493 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(9) \times 3!)) \\
 54494 &:= (((5! \times F(F(4))) - F(F(F(4)))) \times F(9)) + F(4!) \\
 54495 &:= (((- (5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F((F(4)!)) + F(9))) \times 5) \\
 54496 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F(F(F(4))) + F((F(9) - F(F(6)))))) \\
 54498 &:= (((5 - (F((F(4)!))!) + F(4!)) \times 9) + (F(8))) \\
 54499 &:= (- (5) + (((F(4!)) + F((F(4)!)) \times 9) - 9!)) \\
 54504 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 50)) + 4!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54505 &:= (- (5!) + ((F(F((F(4)!)) - F(F(F((5 + 0!)))))) \times (-5)) \\
 54506 &:= (((5! \times F(4)) \times (5! + 0!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 54507 &:= ((- (5) \times (- (F(F(4))) - F(F(F((5 + 0!)))))) - F(F(7))) \\
 54514 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - ((5 + 1)^{F(4)})) \\
 54522 &:= ((- ((5! - F(4))) \times F(F((5 + 2)))) \times (-2)) \\
 54525 &:= (5 \times (((F(F((F(4)!)) \times 5)^2) - 5!)) \\
 54527 &:= (5 + (((F(4) - 5!) \times (-2)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 \\
 54530 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 0 \\
 54531 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 1 \\
 54532 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 2 \\
 54533 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 3 \\
 54534 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 4 \\
 54535 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 5 \\
 54536 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 6 \\
 54537 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 7 \\
 54538 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 8 \\
 54539 &:= -5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times 5 - F(F(F(3!)))) + 9 \\
 \\
 54543 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (- (5) + (4! \times F(3!)))) \\
 54544 &:= ((((5! - F((F(4)!)) + 5!)^{F(F(4))} + ((F(4)!))! \\
 54545 &:= (((- (5) - (F(F(4))^5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 5) \\
 54545 &:= (((- (5) - (F(F(4))^5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 5) \\
 54546 &:= (- ((5! + 4!)) + (- (5) \times (F((F(4)!)) - F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 54547 &:= ((- (5) \times (F((4 + 5)) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - F(7)) \\
 54552 &:= (5! - (((F(4))!^5) \times (- (5 + 2))) \\
 54555 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (5! + (55))) \\
 54556 &:= ((- (54) - 5!) - (- (5) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 54557 &:= (F((5 + (F(4)!)) \times ((5! \times 5) + F(7))) \\
 54564 &:= (- (5!) + ((4 + 5!) \times (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 54565 &:= (- (5!) + ((- ((4 + 5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 54569 &:= (((5 + 4)^5) + ((F(6))! / (-9)) \\
 54570 &:= (- (5) \times ((F(F(4))^5) - F(F((7 + 0!)))) \\
 54573 &:= ((5! - (((F(4))!^5) \times (-7))) + F(F(3!)) \\
 54574 &:= (- ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) + (- (5) \times 7!)) + (F((F(4)!))!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$54575 := (- (5!) + ((F(F((F(4) + (5)))))) - 7) \times 5))$$

$$54578 := (-((5! - F(4))) + (- (5) \times (7 - F(F(8))))))$$

$$54580 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 0$$

$$54581 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 1$$

$$54582 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 2$$

$$54583 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 3$$

$$54584 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 4$$

$$54585 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 5$$

$$54586 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 6$$

$$54587 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 7$$

$$54588 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 8$$

$$54589 := -5 \times (F(4)! \times 5 - F(F(8))) + 9$$

$$54590 := (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - ((- (5) + F(9)) - 0!))$$

$$54592 := ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - (5! + ((9 \times 2)))$$

$$54593 := ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - (5! + (F(9)/F(3))))$$

$$54595 := (- (5!) + ((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(- ((5 - 9)))) \times 5))$$

$$54596 := -((F((5 + (F(4)!)) + (- (5) \times (- (9) + F(F(F(6))))))))$$

$$54597 := ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - (- ((5 - 9)!)) - F(7))$$

$$54598 := ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - ((5! - 9) + F(8)))$$

$$54600 := (- (5) \times ((4! - F(F(F(6)))) + (0! + 0!)))$$

$$54602 := ((- (5) \times (4! - F(F(F(6)))))) - F(((0! + 2)!))$$

$$54603 := ((- (5) \times (4! - F(F(F(6)))))) - (0! + 3!))$$

$$54604 := ((- (5!) - (F(4)!)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (- (0! + (4))))))$$

$$54606 := (- ((5! + (4))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (0! - (6))))$$

$$54607 := ((- (5) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - ((F(F(F(6))) - 0!)))) - F(7))$$

$$54608 := ((- (5!) - F(F(4))) - ((- (6) + 0!) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$54609 := ((- (5) \times (4! - F(F(F(6)))))) - ((0 \times 9)!)$$

$$54610 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 0$$

$$54611 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 1$$

$$54612 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 2$$

$$54613 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 3$$

$$54614 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 4$$

$$54615 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 5$$

$$54616 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 6$$

$$54617 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 7$$

$$54618 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 8$$

$$54619 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6 \times 1)))) + 9$$

$$54620 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 0$$

$$54621 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 1$$

$$54622 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 2$$

$$54623 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 3$$

$$54624 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 4$$

$$54625 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 5$$

$$54626 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 6$$

$$54627 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 7$$

$$54628 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 8$$

$$54629 := 5 \times (-4! + F(F(F(6))) + 2) + 9$$

$$54630 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 0$$

$$54631 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 1$$

$$54632 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 2$$

$$54633 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 3$$

$$54634 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 4$$

$$54635 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 5$$

$$54636 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 6$$

$$54637 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 7$$

$$54638 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 8$$

$$54639 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) + 9$$

$$54640 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 0$$

$$54641 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 1$$

$$54642 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 2$$

$$54643 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 3$$

$$54644 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 4$$

$$54645 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 5$$

$$54646 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 6$$

$$54647 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 7$$

$$54648 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 8$$

$$54649 := 5 \times (F(4)! + F(F(F(6))) - 4!) + 9$$

$$54650 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 0$$

$$54651 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 1$$

$$54652 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 2$$

$$54653 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 3$$

$$54654 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 4$$

$$54655 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 5$$

$$54656 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 6$$

$$54657 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 7$$

$$54658 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 8$$

$$54659 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5! + 9$$

$$54660 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$54661 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$54662 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$54663 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$54664 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$54665 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$54666 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$54667 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$54668 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$54669 := 5 \times (-F(4)! - F(6) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$54670 := (-5) \times ((4 + F(6)) - F(F((7 + 0!))))$$

$$54673 := ((-5!) - (-4!) \times F(F(6))) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)})$$

$$54674 := (((-5!) + F(4!)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (-7! / F(F(4)))$$

$$54676 := ((((-5!) + F(4!)) / (-6)) \times (-7)) + (6!)$$

$$54677 := ((-5) \times (F((F(4)!) - F((F(6) + F(7))))) - F(7))$$

$$54679 := (((5!^{F(4)}) + (F(6)!)) + (-7 - F(9)))$$

$$54682 := (((5! + 4) \times F(F(6))) \times F(8)) - 2$$

$$54683 := (((5! + 4) \times F(F(6))) \times F(8)) - F(F(3))$$

$$54684 := (((5^{F(4)!}) \times F(F(6))) - (F(8))) / (F(4)!)$$

$$54690 := (-5) \times (F((F(4)!) - F(F(F((6 + (9 \times 0)))))))$$

$$54691 := (((-5!) + F(F(F(4)))) + (6!)) \times 91$$

$$54692 := ((-5) \times (-((F(4))!) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9) \times (-2)))$$

$$54693 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) + (F(6))!) - (9 \times 3))$$

$$54694 := (((5!/4!) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (9 \times 4))$$

$$54697 := ((-5) \times (-((F(4))!) - F(F(F(6)))) - (9 \times 7))$$

$$54698 := (5 + ((F((-4) + F(F(6)))) \times 9) + 8!)$$

$$54699 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(6))) - (9!/(-9)))$$

$$54700 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 0$$

$$54701 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 1$$

$$54702 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 2$$

$$54703 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 3$$

$$54704 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 4$$

$$54705 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 5$$

$$54706 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 6$$

$$54707 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 7$$

$$54708 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 8$$

$$54709 := 5 \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7 + 0!))) + 9$$

$$54714 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) + ((7 + 1))!) - (F(4))!)$$

$$54715 := ((5!^{F(F(4))}) + (((7 + 1))! - (5)))$$

$$54720 := ((5!^{F(F(4))}) + ((7 + ((2 \times 0))!))!)$$

$$54721 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) + ((7 + F(2)))!) + 1)$$

$$54722 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) + ((7 + F(2)))!) + 2)$$

$$54723 := ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - (F(2) + 3!))$$

$$54727 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) + 7) + ((F(2) + (7)))!)$$

$$54728 := ((5!^{F(F(4))}) - ((7! + F(2)) \times (-8)))$$

$$54729 := ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) - (F(2)^9!))$$

$$54730 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 0$$

$$54731 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 1$$

$$54732 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 2$$

$$54733 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 3$$

$$54734 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 4$$

$$54735 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 5$$

$$54736 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 6$$

$$54737 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 7$$

$$54738 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 8$$

$$54739 := 5!/4! \times F(7 \times 3) + 9$$

$$54740 := (-5) \times ((F(F(4)) + F((7 \times F(4)))) \times (-0!))$$

$$54742 := ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (4!/2))$$

$$54746 := ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (4! - F(6)))$$

$$54747 := ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (4! - (7)))$$

$$54748 := ((5!^{F(F(4))}) - (-((7 \times 4) - 8!))$$

$$54750 := (5 \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) + (5 - 0!)))$$

$$54754 := ((5 \times F(F((4 \times (7 - 5)))))) + (4!))$$

$$54760 := (-5) \times (((F(4))! + F((F(7) + F(6)))) \times (-0!))$$

$$54761 := ((5 \times ((F(4))! + F((F(7) + F(6)))))) + 1$$

$$54762 := ((5 \times ((F(4))! + F((F(7) + F(6)))))) + 2$$

$$54763 := (((-5) + F(4!)) - (7!)) + ((F(6))!/3)$$

$$54767 := ((5 \times ((F(4))! + F((F(7) + F(6)))))) + 7$$

$$54768 := ((5!^{F(F(4))}) - ((7! + (6)) \times (-8)))$$

$$54769 := ((5! \times 4) + (F(F(7)))^{F(-6+9)})$$

$$54770 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 0$$

$$54771 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 1$$

$$54772 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 2$$

$$54773 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 3$$

$$54774 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 4$$

$$54775 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 5$$

$$54776 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 6$$

$$54777 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 7$$

$$54778 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 8$$

$$54779 := 5 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(-7 + F(7)))))) + 9$$

$$54783 := ((-5) \times ((4 - F(7)) - F(F(8)))) + F(3!))$$

$$54784 := (((5 \times 4!) - F(7)) \times (8^{F(4)}))$$

$$54785 := (((5! + F(4!)) + F(F(7))) + (8!/5))$$

$$54786 := ((5 \times F((F(4) \times 7))) + (8!/6!))$$

$$54790 := (-5) \times ((F(F(F(4))) - F(7)) - F(F((9 - 0!))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54792 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + ((7 \times 9) - F(2))) \\ 54793 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4)))))) \times F(F(7))) - (-9!/(3)!)) \\ 54794 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4)!)) + F(-(F(7) - F(9)))))) + (4!)) \\ 54797 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(7))) + (9 - 7)) \\ 54798 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + ((F(7) + F(9)) + F(8))) \\ 54799 &:= (((5! + 4) \times F(7)) \times F(9)) - 9 \\ 54800 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (F((8 - 0!) + 0!))) \\ 54803 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F((8 - 0!)))) + F(3!)) \\ 54804 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))) + F((0! + F((F(4)!)))))) \\ 54809 &:= ((5 \times (F((F(4)!)) + ((F(F(8)) + 0!)))) + F(9)) \\ 54810 &:= (5 \times (((F(4)! + F(F(8))) + 10)) \\ 54811 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + (81 \times 1)) \\ 54812 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + (81 + F(2))) \\ 54813 &:= ((5 \times (F(F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))) - (1 + F(F(3!)))) \\ 54814 &:= ((5 \times (F(F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))) + (-1) \times F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\ 54815 &:= (5! + (((F(4)! - F(F(8))) + 1) \times (-5))) \\ 54816 &:= ((-5) \times (-4! - F(F(8)))) - F((1 + F(6))) \\ 54817 &:= ((5 \times (F(F((F(4)!)) + ((F(F(8)) - 1)))) - F(7)) \\ 54819 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + F(-(8 - 19))) \\ 54820 &:= (-5) \times ((-4! - F(F(8))) + ((2 + 0!)!)) \\ 54823 &:= ((5 \times (F(F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))) - (2 \times 3!)) \\ 54824 &:= ((5 \times ((F(4)! + F(F(8)))) + (2^{F(4)!})) \\ 54825 &:= (((-5) + 4!) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) \times 5)) \\ 54826 &:= ((5! - 4!) - (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) - (6)))) \\ 54827 &:= ((-5) \times ((-4! - F(F(8))) + 2)) - F(7) \\ 54828 &:= ((-5) \times (-4! - F(F(8)))) - (F(2) + F(8)) \\ \\ 54830 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 0 \\ 54831 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 1 \\ 54832 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 2 \\ 54833 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 3 \\ 54834 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 4 \\ 54835 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 5 \\ 54836 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 6 \\ 54837 &:= 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$54838 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 8$$

$$54839 := 5 \times (-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) + 9$$

$$54840 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 0$$

$$54841 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 1$$

$$54842 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 2$$

$$54843 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 3$$

$$54844 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 4$$

$$54845 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 5$$

$$54846 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 6$$

$$54847 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 7$$

$$54848 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 8$$

$$54849 := 5 \times (-F(F(4)) + F(F(8)) + 4!) + 9$$

$$54850 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 0$$

$$54851 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 1$$

$$54852 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 2$$

$$54853 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 3$$

$$54854 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 4$$

$$54855 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 5$$

$$54856 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 6$$

$$54857 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 7$$

$$54858 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 8$$

$$54859 := 5 \times 4! + F(F(8)) \times 5 + 9$$

$$54860 := (5! - ((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times (-6 + 0!)))$$

$$54862 := ((-5) \times (-4! - F(F(8)))) + (6 \times 2)$$

$$54863 := ((-5) \times (-4! - F(F(8)))) + (F(F(6)) - F(3!))$$

$$54864 := (((5! \times F(4)) + F(8)) \times 6) \times 4!$$

$$54865 := ((((-5) + 4!) + F(F(8))) + F(6)) \times 5$$

$$54866 := (((5! \times 4!) + F(F(8))) + (6!)) + (F(6))!$$

$$54867 := (((5!^{F(F(4))}) + 8!) + (F(F(6)) \times 7))$$

$$54868 := (5! + (((F(4) + F(F(8))) \times 6) - F(F(8))))$$

$$54869 := (((5!/4!) \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) + F(9))$$

$$54870 := (-5) \times ((F(F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(8)) + 7)) \times (-0!))$$

$$54870 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 0$$

$$54871 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 1$$

$$54872 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 2$$

$$54873 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 3$$

$$54874 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 4$$

$$54875 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 5$$

$$54876 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 6$$

$$54877 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 7$$

$$54878 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 8$$

$$54879 := 5 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) + 7) + 9$$

$$54880 := (-5) \times ((4 - F(F(8))) - F((8 + 0!)))$$

$$54882 := ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (8 \times (F(8) - 2)))$$

$$54883 := ((-5) \times (F(4) - F(F(8)))) - (-F(8)) \times F(3!))$$

$$54885 := (((5! - F((F(4) + 8))) + F(F(8))) \times 5)$$

$$54886 := ((5 \times ((F(4)! + F(F(8)))) + (F(8) \times 6))$$

$$54888 := ((5!^{F(4)}) - ((-8) \times F(8)) - 8!)$$

$$54889 := ((-5) \times ((F(4)! - F(F(8)))) + (F(8) \times 9))$$

$$54890 := (-5) \times ((-4!) - F(F(8))) - (9 - 0!))$$

$$54893 := ((-5) \times ((F(4) - F(F(8))) - F(9))) + F(3!))$$

$$54897 := ((-5) \times (-4!) - F(F(8))) + (F(9) + F(7))$$

$$54900 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 00$$

$$54901 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 01$$

$$54902 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 02$$

$$54903 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 03$$

$$54904 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 04$$

$$54905 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 05$$

$$54906 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 06$$

$$54907 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 07$$

$$54908 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 08$$

$$54909 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 09$$

$$54910 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 10$$

$$54911 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(9)) + 11$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54912 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 12 \\ 54913 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 13 \\ 54914 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 14 \\ 54915 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 15 \\ 54916 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 16 \\ 54917 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 17 \\ 54918 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 18 \\ 54919 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 19 \\ 54920 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 20 \\ 54921 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 21 \\ 54922 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 22 \\ 54923 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 23 \\ 54924 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 24 \\ 54925 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 25 \\ 54926 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 26 \\ 54927 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 27 \\ 54928 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 28 \\ 54929 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 29 \\ 54930 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 30 \\ 54931 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 31 \\ 54932 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 32 \\ 54933 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 33 \\ 54934 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 34 \\ 54935 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 35 \\ 54936 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 36 \\ 54937 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 37 \\ 54938 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 38 \\ 54939 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 39 \\ 54940 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 40 \\ 54941 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 41 \\ 54942 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 42 \\ 54943 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 43 \\ 54944 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 44 \\ 54945 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 45 \\ 54946 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 46 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54947 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 47 \\ 54948 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 48 \\ 54949 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 49 \\ 54950 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 50 \\ 54951 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 51 \\ 54952 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 52 \\ 54953 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 53 \\ 54954 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 54 \\ 54955 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 55 \\ 54956 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 56 \\ 54957 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 57 \\ 54958 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 58 \\ 54959 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 59 \\ 54960 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 60 \\ 54961 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 61 \\ 54962 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 62 \\ 54963 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 63 \\ 54964 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 64 \\ 54965 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 65 \\ 54966 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 66 \\ 54967 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 67 \\ 54968 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 68 \\ 54969 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 69 \\ 54970 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 70 \\ 54971 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 71 \\ 54972 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 72 \\ 54973 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 73 \\ 54974 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 74 \\ 54975 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 75 \\ 54976 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 76 \\ 54977 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 77 \\ 54978 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 78 \\ 54979 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 79 \\ 54980 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 80 \\ 54981 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 81 \end{aligned}$$

$$54982 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 82$$

$$54983 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 83$$

$$54984 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 84$$

$$54985 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 85$$

$$54986 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 86$$

$$54987 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 87$$

$$54988 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 88$$

$$54989 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 89$$

$$54990 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 90$$

$$54991 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 91$$

$$54992 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 92$$

$$54993 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 93$$

$$54994 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 94$$

$$54995 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 95$$

$$54996 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 96$$

$$54997 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 97$$

$$54998 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 98$$

$$54999 := 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4!)))) + F(9)) + 99$$

$$55054 := ((550 \times 5!) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$55073 := (((5! \times (5! + 0!)) + F(F(7))) + (F(3)!))$$

$$55097 := ((-5) \times (-5! - F(F(-(0! - 9)))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$55107 := ((5 \times F(F(F((5 + 1)))) + (F((0! + F(7))))$$

$$55223 := (((-5) - (5! \times (-2)))^2) - F(3)$$

$$55224 := (((-5) - (5! \times (-2)))^2) - F(F(F(4)))$$

$$55225 := ((-5) - (5! \times (-2)))^{F(-2+5)}$$

$$55233 := (((-5) - (5! \times (-2)))^{F(3)} + F(3!))$$

$$55234 := ((5 \times F(F(F((5 - 2)!))) + (F(F(3!)) \times 4!))$$

$$55246 := (((-5) - (5! \times (-2)))^{F(F(4))} + F(F(6)))$$

$$55265 := (((5! - F((5 + 2))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5)$$

$$55292 := (((5! \times 5) + F(2)) \times 92)$$

$$55304 := ((-5) \times ((-5! - F(F(F(3!)))) + 0!)) - F(F((F(4)!)))$$

$$55305 := (((5! - 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 05)$$

$$55308 := ((-5) \times (-5! - F(F(F(3!)))) - (0! + F(8)))$$

$$55309 := ((-5) \times (-5! - F(F(F(3!)))) - F(-(0! - 9)))$$

$$55314 := ((-5) \times ((-5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - 1) - F(F((F(4)!)))$$

$$55315 := (-5) \times (-((5! - 3) - F(F(F((1 + 5))))))$$

$$55317 := ((-5) \times (-5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - F((1 \times 7))$$

$$55320 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 0$$

$$55321 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 1$$

$$55322 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 2$$

$$55323 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 3$$

$$55324 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 4$$

$$55325 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 5$$

$$55326 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 6$$

$$55327 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 7$$

$$55328 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 8$$

$$55329 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 2) + 9$$

$$55330 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 0$$

$$55331 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 1$$

$$55332 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 2$$

$$55333 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 3$$

$$55334 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 4$$

$$55335 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 5$$

$$55336 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 6$$

$$55337 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 7$$

$$55338 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 8$$

$$55339 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3 + 3)))) + 9$$

$$55340 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 0$$

$$55341 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 1$$

$$55342 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 2$$

$$55343 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 3$$

$$55344 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 4$$

$$55345 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 5$$

$$55346 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 6$$

$$55347 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 7$$

$$55348 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 8$$

$$55349 := 5 \times (5! + F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4))) + 9$$

$$55360 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$55361 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$55362 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$55363 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$55364 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$55365 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$55366 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$55367 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$55368 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$55369 := 5 \times (5! + 3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$55370 := (-5) \times ((-5!) - F(3!)) - F(F((7 + 0!)))$$

$$55373 := ((-5) \times ((-5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - 7) + F(3!)$$

$$55374 := ((5 + (5 - F(3)))! \times (7! - (F(4))!))$$

$$55384 := ((-5) \times (-((5! + 3!)) - F(F(8))) + (4!))$$

$$55385 := (((5! + 5) + 3!) + F(F(8))) \times 5$$

$$55386 := ((-5) \times (-5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (8!/6!)$$

$$55396 := ((-5) \times ((-5!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - 9) + (F(F(6)))$$

$$55423 := ((-5) \times (5 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (-2 + 3!))$$

$$55424 := ((-5) \times (5 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (-F(2) + ((F(4))!))$$

$$55425 := ((-5) \times (5 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (((F(2) + 5))!))$$

$$55426 := ((-5) \times (5 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F(2) + 6!))$$

$$55430 := (-5) \times (((-5!) - F(F((F(4))!))) - F(F(F(3!)))) + 0!$$

$$55433 := (-5) + (((5 + (F(4))!))! / (3!)! - F(3))$$

$$55434 := (((5! \times 5!) - (F(4))!) + (F(3))!) + ((F(4))!)$$

$$55435 := (-5) - ((-5) - (F(4))!) \times ((F(3) + 5))!$$

$$55436 := (((5! \times 5!) - 4) + 3!) + (F(6))!$$

$$55437 := ((5 \times F(F((5 + F(4)))) + ((3!)! - F(7)))$$

$$55438 := (((5! \times 5!) - F(F(4))) + 3!) + 8!$$

$$55439 := (-5) + ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F(F(3!)) \times F(9)))$$

$$55440 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4))! + 0$$

$$55441 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4))! + 1$$

$$55442 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4))! + 2$$

$$55443 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4))! + 3$$

$$55444 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 4$$

$$55445 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 5$$

$$55446 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 6$$

$$55447 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 7$$

$$55448 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 8$$

$$55449 := 5! \times (5! + F(4)!) + F(F(4)!)! + 9$$

$$55450 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 0$$

$$55451 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 1$$

$$55452 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 2$$

$$55453 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 3$$

$$55454 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 4$$

$$55455 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 5$$

$$55456 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 6$$

$$55457 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 7$$

$$55458 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 8$$

$$55459 := 5! + 5 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!))) + 5!) + 9$$

$$55463 := (5 + ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + (F(6) + 3!!))$$

$$55464 := ((5! \times (5! + (F(4)!) + ((F(6)!) + (4!))))$$

$$55465 := (5! - (((5! + F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)))$$

$$55466 := (5 - (((5 + (F(4)!)!)/(-6!) - (F(F(6)))))$$

$$55469 := ((-5) + F((5!/4)))/(6 + 9)$$

$$55473 := ((5 + ((5 - F(F(4))))!) \times (7! + 3))$$

$$55474 := ((-5) \times (-5! - F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + F((F(7) - F(F(F(4)))))$$

$$55475 := (-5) \times ((-5) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - F((7 + 5)))$$

$$55479 := (5 + (((5 + (F(4)!) \times 7!) + F(9)))$$

$$55483 := ((-5) \times (-5) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (8 + 3!!))$$

$$55488 := ((-5!) + F((-5) + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (8 \times 8))$$

$$55494 := ((-5) \times ((-5!) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(9)) - (F(4)!)!$$

$$55495 := (5! - (((5! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + 9) \times (-5))$$

$$55587 := (((5! - (5^5)) + F(F(8))) \times 7)$$

$$55630 := (F((5!/5)) + ((F(F(6))^3 + 0!))$$

$$55634 := ((F((5!/5)) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(3)!)!)/(-4!))$$

$$55664 := ((5! \times (5! - F(F(6)))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 4))$$

$$55665 := ((-5) \times (5 - F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) \times 5!))$$

$$55667 := (((5! \times (5! + F(6))) + (F(6))!) - F(7))$$

$$55673 := (((5! \times 5!) + (F(6))!) + F(F(7))) + 3!!$$

$$55676 := (5 + ((5 + 6) \times (7! + F(F(6)))))$$

$$55680 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 0$$

$$55681 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 1$$

$$55682 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 2$$

$$55683 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 3$$

$$55684 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 4$$

$$55685 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 5$$

$$55686 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 6$$

$$55687 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 7$$

$$55688 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 8$$

$$55689 := 5! \times (5! + F(6)) + 8! + 9$$

$$55697 := (5 + (((5! + (6)) \times F(9)) \times F(7)))$$

$$55704 := (((5! + 5!) \times (F(F(7)) - 0!)) + (4!))$$

$$55728 := (F((5!/5)) + (F(7) \times (-((2 - 8))))!))$$

$$55734 := (((5! \times 5!) - 7!) + 3!) + F(4!))$$

$$55736 := (F((5!/5)) - ((-F(7)) \times (3!)!) - F(6)))$$

$$55741 := (F((5!/5)) + (F(7) \times (((F(4))!)! + 1)))$$

$$55743 := (((5! \times 5!) + F((F(7) + (F(4))!))) \times 3)$$

$$55754 := ((F((5!/5)) - (F(7) \times 5!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$55773 := (((5! + 5!) \times F(F(7))) + (-7) \times F(F(3!)))$$

$$55774 := (-5!) + (((5! \times F(F(7))) - F(7)) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$55775 := (-5!) - ((F(F((-5) + F(7))) + F(F(7))) \times (-5))$$

$$55780 := (-5!) - (-5) \times ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + 0!))$$

$$55783 := (-5!) + ((5 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)))) + F(3!))$$

$$55784 := (-5!) + (((5! \times F(F(7))) - 8) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$55834 := ((-5) \times (-5!) - F(F(8))) - (F(F(3!)) \times (-4!))$$

$$55837 := (5! + ((5 \times F(F(8))) + F((3 + F(7)))))$$

$$55848 := (((5! \times 58) + F(F((F(4))!))) \times 8)$$

$$55890 := (((5! \times 5) + F(8)) \times 90)$$

$$55895 := (-5) \times (-F((5 + 8))) - F(F(F((F((9 - 5))!))))$$

$$55920 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 0$$

$$55921 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 1$$

$$55922 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 2$$

$$55923 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 3$$

$$55924 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 4$$

$$55925 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 5$$

$$55926 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 6$$

$$55927 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 7$$

$$55928 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 8$$

$$55929 := (5! + 5!) \times F(F(9 - 2)) + 9$$

$$55943 := (((5^{F(-5+9)!}) - F(F(4))) + (F(3)!))!$$

$$55944 := (((5! + 5!) \times F((9 + 4))) + 4!)$$

$$55945 := ((5^{F(-5+9)!}) + (((F(4) + (5))))!)$$

$$55946 := (((5^{F(-5+9)!}) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F(6)!))!$$

$$55948 := ((5^{F(-5+9)!}) + ((F(4) + 8!)))$$

$$55966 := ((5^{F(-5+9)!}) + (((F(6))! + F(F(6)))))$$

$$56040 := (5! \times ((F(F((F(6) - 0!))) \times F(F(4))) + 0!))$$

$$56065 := (((5^6) + (F(06)))! + 5!)$$

$$56134 := ((5 + F(F(6))) \times (-1 + ((3!)! \times F(4))))$$

$$56147 := ((5 + ((6! - 1) \times (F(4))!)) \times F(7))$$

$$56153 := (F((5 + F(6))) \times (1 + (5! \times F(3))))$$

$$56173 := ((5 + F(6)) \times ((1 + 7!) - 3!))$$

$$56174 := (((5 + F(F((6 + 1)))) \times F(F(7))) + ((F(4))!))!$$

$$56178 := (((5^6) + F(F((1 \times 7)))) + 8!)$$

$$56186 := ((-((5! - ((6 + 1)!)) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$56187 := ((((-5!) + (F(6))!) + 1) + F(F(8))) + (7!))$$

$$56233 := (((5^{F(6)-F(2)}) - F(F(F(3)))) - F(F(F(3))))$$

$$56234 := ((-((5! \times (F(6) + F(2)))) + F(F(F(3)))) + F(4!))$$

$$56254 := (((5 \times (F(6))!)/(-2 - 5)) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$56273 := (5! + (F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) \times (F(F(7)) + F(3))))$$

$$56274 := (5! + (((F(F(6)) \times 2) \times F(F(7))) + F(4!)))$$

$$56286 := ((5! + ((F(F(6))^2) \times F(8))) \times 6)$$

$$56294 := ((-5) - F((F(F(6)) - 2))) + (9!/(F(4))!))$$

- 56306 := ((5! × (F((F(6) + 3!)) + 0!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 56307 := (((F(((−(5) + F(6)))!))! + F(F(F(3!)))) + (0! + 7!))
- 56320 := ((5! + F(6)) × ((F(F(3!))²) − 0!))
- 56334 := ((5! + ((F(F(6))³) + F(3!))) × (F(4))!)
- 56335 := (((5! − F(F(F(6)))) − (F(F(3!))^{F(3)})) × (−5))
- 56343 := (((5! − F(F(6))) + F((3! × F(4)))) × F(F(3!)))
- 56344 := (((−(5) + (F(F(6))³)) + ((F(4))!))! + F(4!))
- 56346 := (((−((5! × F(6))) − F(3!)) + F(4!)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 56347 := ((−((5! × F(6))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(4!) − 7)))
- 56348 := ((−((5! × F(6)) + 3!)) + F(4!)) + F(F(8)))
- 56349 := ((F((5!/6)) + (F(F(3!)) × (−4!))) × 9)
- 56354 := ((−((5! × F(6))) + F(F((3 + 5)))) + F(4!))
- 56357 := (((−(5) − F(6)) + ((F(3!))!/5)) × 7)
- 56368 := ((5 + F(F(6))) × ((3 × 6!) + 8))
- 56384 := ((−((5! − 6!)) × F(F(3!))) − (F(F(8)) × (−4)))
- 56386 := (((5⁶) + (F(3!))!) − (−(F(8)) × F(F(6))))
- 56395 := (5 × (F(F(F(6))) + (3 × (−(9) + 5!))))
- 56396 := (F(F(F(((−(5) + F(6)))!))) − (((3!)! + 9!)/(−F(6))))
- 56397 := (5! + (((6! × 3!) + 9) × F(7)))
- 56400 := ((−(5!) − F(F(6))) × (−400))
- 56424 := (((5! − F(6)) × F(F((F(4))!))) − F(2)) × 4!
- 56426 := ((5! + F(F(F(6)))) − (((F(4)²)!)/(−F(6))))
- 56427 := (((5! + F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(4))!))! + ((F(2) + 7!)))
- 56433 := ((5 + F(6)) × (((F(4))! × (3!)! + F(F(3!))))
- 56434 := (((5 × F(F(F(6)))) + (4!)) − ((F(3!))!/(−4!)))
- 56437 := ((−((5 + 6)) + F(4!)) + ((F(3) × 7!)))
- 56439 := (((5! − F(6)) × 4!) × F(F(3!))) − 9)
- 56442 := (−(5) + (((F(6))!/4) + F(4!)) − F(2))
- 56443 := (−(5) − (((F(6))!/(−4)) − F((4 × 3!))))
- 56444 := (((5! × F(F(6))) × 4) − 4) + F(4!))
- 56447 := (((5 − 6) + F(4!)) + (F(F(4)) × 7!))
- 56453 := (5 − (−(F(6)) × (((F(4))!⁵) − 3!)))
- 56454 := (((−(5!) − (F(6))!)/F(4)) × (−5)) − F(F(F((F(4))!)))
- 56455 := (((−(5) − (F(6))!) × (F(F(4)) + (5)))/(−5))
- 56456 := ((5! + ((F(6))! × F(F((F(4))!))))/(5!/F(6)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 56457 &:= (-5) + ((F(F(F(6))) - ((4! \times 5!)) \times 7)) \\
 56462 &:= (((5 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((4! \times 6!))) \times 2) \\
 56464 &:= (-5) + (((F(6)!/4) + F(F(6))) + F(4!)) \\
 56466 &:= ((-5!) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4!) - ((F(6) + 6!)))) \\
 56467 &:= (-5) - (((6! + 4) \times (-6)) \times F(7)) \\
 56468 &:= (((-(5! + 6!)) + F(4!)) - 6) + F(F(8)) \\
 56474 &:= ((-(5! + 6!)) + F(4!)) + F((7 \times F(4))) \\
 56475 &:= (((5! + F(F(F(6)))) + (-4) + F(F(7))) \times 5) \\
 56477 &:= (5 - (((6! - 4!) - 7!) \times F(7))) \\
 56485 &:= ((5 - 6!) \times ((-4) \times F(8)) + (5)) \\
 56487 &:= (((5 \times (F(6)!)/F(4)) - F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) \\
 56494 &:= ((-(5! - 6!)) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 94 \\
 56495 &:= (((-5!) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F((4 + 9)))) \times (-5) \\
 56499 &:= (-5!) + ((-F(F(6))) + ((F(4)!)) \times (9 \times 9)) \\
 \\
 56530 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 0 \\
 56531 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 1 \\
 56532 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 2 \\
 56533 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 3 \\
 56534 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 4 \\
 56535 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 5 \\
 56536 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 6 \\
 56537 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 7 \\
 56538 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 8 \\
 56539 &:= 5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! \times 3) + 9 \\
 \\
 56545 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (5! + (F(4)^5)))) \\
 56547 &:= (5! - (((F(6)!)/(-5)) + F(4)) \times 7) \\
 56574 &:= (5! - (((F(6)!)/(-5)) \times 7) - (F(4)!)) \\
 56575 &:= (((5 + (F(6)!)/(-5)) \times (-7)) + 5!) \\
 56576 &:= (((5! + F(6)) \times (5! + 7)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 56584 &:= (((-5) - 6!) - 5) + F(F(8)) + F(4!) \\
 56594 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((5 + 9)))) - F(F((F(4)!)))) \\
 56623 &:= (((5 + F((F(F(6)) - F(6))))^2) - F(F(3!))) \\
 56634 &:= (((5 \times F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((3!) - F(4!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56635 &:= (-5) \times ((-F(F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) + (-3 \times 5!)) \\56639 &:= (-5) + (((6! - 6)^{F(3)})/9) \\56640 &:= ((5! \times F(F(6))) - (-F(6) \times F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 0!)))) \\56644 &:= (((5! \times 6) - 6)/F(4))^{F(F(4))} \\56645 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6)!/F(F((F(4)!))) - 5)) \\56649 &:= (5 + (((6! - 6)^{F(F(4))})/9)) \\56650 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6)!/F(F((5 + 0!)))) \\56663 &:= (((5^6) + (F(6)!)) + (6! - F(3))) \\56664 &:= (((5^6) + (F(6)!)) + (6!)) - F(F(F(4))) \\56665 &:= (((5^6) + (F(6)!)) - (-6 \times 5!)) \\56665 &:= (((5^6) + (F(6)!)) - (-6 \times 5!)) \\56678 &:= (((5^6) + 6!) + F(7)) + 8! \\56684 &:= (((-5) \times F(F(6))) \times 6) + F(F(8)) + F(4!) \\56686 &:= (((5^6) + (F(6)!)) + ((F(8) + 6!))) \\56704 &:= ((-F((5!/F(6)))) + F(F((7 + 0!))) + F(4!)) \\56714 &:= (((5! - 6!) + F(F((7 + 1)))) + F(4!)) \\56735 &:= (5! - ((F(F(F(6))) + (F((7 \times F(3)))) \times (-5))) \\56736 &:= ((F((-5) + F(6))) \times 7!) + (3!^6) \\56737 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7)))) - (F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(7)))) \\56745 &:= ((5! + 6) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(4)^5))) \\56749 &:= ((5 + 6) \times (7 + (F(4!)/9))) \\56754 &:= (((5 + 6) \times (7! + 5!)) - (F(4)!)) \\56760 &:= -((5! + (6! \times ((F(7) \times (-6)) - 0!))) \\56784 &:= ((-((5! - 6) \times F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4)!)) \\56830 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(8) \times (F(F(3!)) - 0!))) \\56835 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (-F(F(8)))/(F(F(3!)) + 5))) \\56864 &:= (((5 \times 6!)/(-8) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4!)) \\56873 &:= (((F((5 + F(6))) + 8) \times F(F(7))) + 3!) \\56914 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (91 \times 4!)) \\56940 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) \times F(((F(4)! + 0!)))) \\56944 &:= ((((-5!) + (F(6)!)) \times F(9))/4!) - (F(4)!)) \\56945 &:= ((((-5!) + (F(6)!)) \times F(9))/4!) - 5) \\56952 &:= (-((5^6) + ((9!/5) + F(2))) \\56953 &:= (-((5^6) + ((9!/5) + F(3)))\end{aligned}$$

- 56954 := $(-(5^6) + ((9!/5) + F(4)))$
 56968 := $(((-5!) + F(F(6))) \times (F(9) - 6!)) - F(F(8)))$
 56976 := $(-5!) - (((F(6) \times (-9)) \times F(F(7))) - (F(6)!))$
 56978 := $(-(5! \times (6! - 9))) - (-F(7) \times F(F(8)))$
 57036 := $((5! \times (F(7) - 0!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-6)$
 57044 := $((F(((5 + F(7)) + 0!)) \times 4) + (F((F(4)!)))$
 57077 := $(5 + ((F(F(7)) - 0!) \times (F(F(7)) + F(7))))$
 57120 := $((((5 + F(F(7))) + 1)^2) - 0!)$
 57146 := $((5! \times (F((F(7) + 1)) + F((F(4)!)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
 57155 := $((5! + F((F(7) + 1))) \times (5! - 5))$
 57177 := $(57 - (-((17)!)/(F(7)!))$
 57194 := $((-5!) + F(F((7 + (1^9)))) + F(4!))$
 57224 := $(-5!) + (7 \times (2^{F(F(2)+F(4)!)}))$
 57235 := $((((5! - F(7))^2) - F(3)) \times 5)$
 57242 := $(5! - (((F(7) \times F(2))^4) \times (-2)))$
 57243 := $((-(5! - (7^2))) + F(4!)) + F(F(F(3!)))$
 57244 := $((-(5 \times 7) + F(-(F(2) - 4!))) \times F(F(4)))$
 57245 := $((5! - F(7))^{-2+4}) \times 5$
 57246 := $((57 + F(2)) \times F((4! - F(6))))$
 57248 := $((((-5) \times F(7)) - F(2)) + F(4!)) + F(F(8))$
 57253 := $((((5! - F(7))^2) \times 5) + F(3!))$
 57274 := $((((5! \times F(7)) - 2) \times 7) + F(4!))$
 57284 := $(((-5) \times (7 - F(2))) + F(F(8))) + F(4!)$
 57285 := $((((5! - F(7))^2) + 8) \times 5)$
 57306 := $((5 - F(7)) + F(((3 + 0!))) + F(F(F(6))))$
 57307 := $((F(F((-5) + F(7))) + F(((3 + 0!))) - 7)$
 57308 := $(((-5) + F(((7 - 3)!)) - 0!) + F(F(8)))$
 57309 := $((-5) + F(((7 - 3)!)) + F(F(-(0! - 9))))$
 57312 := $(F(F((-5) + F(7))) + ((F(((3 + 1)!)) - 2))$
 57313 := $(F(F((-5) + F(7))) - (F(F(3)) - F(((1 + 3)!)))$
 57314 := $((5 - F((7 - 3))) \times F((-1 + 4!))$
 57315 := $((F(F((-5) + F(7))) + F(F(3))) + F((-((1 - 5)!)))$
 57316 := $((-((5 - 7)) + F(((3 + 1)!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
 57318 := $((5 + F(((7 - 3)!)) - 1) + F(F(8)))$
 57319 := $((5 + F(((7 - 3)!)) + F(F(-(1 - 9))))$

$$\begin{aligned} 57322 &:= (F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + ((F(3!) + F(((2 + 2)!))) \\ 57323 &:= (-5) + ((7 + F((F(F(3!)) + 2))) \times F(3)) \\ 57326 &:= (((5 + 7) + F(((F(3) + 2)!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 57327 &:= ((F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + F(((F(3) + 2)!)) + F(7)) \\ 57332 &:= (((5 + F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(((F(3) + 2)!))) \\ 57333 &:= (((5! \times F(F(7))) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(F(3)) - (F(3!)!)) \\ 57334 &:= ((F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + F(F(3!))) - (F(F(3)) - F(4!)) \\ 57335 &:= ((F((5 + F(7))) + F(F(3!))) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-5)) \\ 57336 &:= ((5! \times F((F(7) - F(3)))) + (3!^6)) \\ 57343 &:= ((F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + F(F(3!))) + (F(4!) + F(3!)) \\ 57344 &:= (((-5) + F(7)) + 3!) \times (4^{F(4)!}) \\ 57346 &:= (((5 \times 7) - 3) + F(4!)) + F(F(F(6))) \\ 57347 &:= (((5! \times F(F(7))) + 3!) \times F(F(4))) - F(7) \\ 57348 &:= ((F(((5 + 7) - 3)) + F(4!)) + F(F(8))) \\ 57353 &:= ((5 \times (F(7)^3)) + F(((5 - F(F(3))))!)) \\ 57354 &:= (F(F((-5) + F(7))) - ((F(3!) \times (-5)) - F(4!)) \\ 57355 &:= (-5) - ((F(F(7)) + 3!) \times (-5! + 5!)) \\ 57358 &:= ((5 + F(F(7))) \times (F(3!) + (F((5 + 8)))) \\ 57360 &:= (-5!) \times ((F(F(7)) - 3!) + (F(6) + 0!)) \\ 57362 &:= (((5 + F(F(7)))^{F(3)} + ((6! - 2))) \\ 57363 &:= (((5 + F(F(7)))^{F(3)} + (6!)) - F(F(3))) \\ 57364 &:= (((5! \times F(F(7))) + (F(3) + 6!)) \times F(F(4))) \\ 57367 &:= ((5 \times ((F(7) + 3) \times 6!)) - F(F(7))) \\ 57374 &:= (((5! \times F(F(7))) + 3!) + 7) \times F(F(4)) \\ 57377 &:= (-5) - ((F(F(7)) + F((3! + F(7)))) \times (-F(7))) \\ 57379 &:= (((5 \times F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) + F(((F(7) - 9)!)) \\ 57384 &:= (((5 \times 7) \times F(3)) + F(F(8))) + F(4!) \\ 57386 &:= (((5! + 7!) \times (F(F(3)) + 8)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 57394 &:= (F(F((-5) + F(7))) + (((3!)! / 9) + F(4!)) \\ 57421 &:= (((5! - F(7)) + F(4!)) + F(21)) \\ 57423 &:= (((5! - F(7)) + F(4!)) + 2) + F(F(F(3!))) \\ 57426 &:= (((5! - 7) + F(4!)) - F(2)) + F(F(F(6))) \\ 57427 &:= (((5! - 7) + F(4!)) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))) \\ 57428 &:= (((5! - 7) + F(4!)) + F(2)) + F(F(8)) \end{aligned}$$

- 57432 := (((5! + F(((7 - F(4))))!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 2)
- 57433 := (((5! - (7)) + F(4!)) + 3!) + F(F(F(3!)))
- 57434 := ((5! + F((7 × F(4)))) + F((3! × 4)))
- 57435 := (F(F((-5) + F(7))) + (((F(4!) + F(F(3))) + 5!)))
- 57436 := (((5! + F(((7 - F(4))))!) + F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 57438 := (((5! + (7)) + F(4!)) - 3) + F(F(8))
- 57440 := (((5! + (7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (F(4!) - 0!))
- 57441 := ((5! + (7)) + (F(F(4)) × F((4! - 1))))
- 57442 := (((5! + (7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((F(4!) + F(2))))
- 57443 := (((5! + F(7)) - (4)) + F(4!)) + F(F(F(3!)))
- 57444 := (((5 × F(7)) + F((4! - F(F(F(4)))))) × F(F(4)))
- 57446 := (((5! + F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) + F(4!)) + F(F(F(6)))
- 57447 := (((5! + F(7)) + F(4!)) + F((F(4) × 7)))
- 57448 := (5! - (((-7) × F(F(4))) - F(4!)) - F(F(8)))
- 57449 := ((F((5 + 7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (F(4!) - 9))
- 57453 := ((5! × (-F(F(7))) + ((F(4)!))!) - F((-5) + F(F(3!))))
- 57454 := (((5! × F(F(7))) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (-5!) - (F((F(4)!))!))
- 57456 := (F((-5) + F(7)) × (4! × (5! - (6))))
- 57458 := ((F((5 + 7)) + F(4!)) + F(F(F((-((5 - 8))))!)))
- 57464 := (5! + ((7 × F(F(4))) × (F(6)⁴)))
- 57466 := (((F((5 + 7)) + F(4!)) + F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))
- 57467 := ((5! × ((-F(F(7))) + ((F(4)!))!) - F(6)) - F(7))
- 57468 := (((5! + F(7)) + F(4!)) + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))
- 57471 := (5! + (7 × ((F(F(4)))^{F(7)}) + 1))
- 57474 := ((5! + F(F(7))) + (((F(4)! + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))}))
- 57475 := (-5) + (((F(F(7)) × F(F(4))) + F(7)) × 5!)
- 57475 := (-5) + (((F(F(7)) × F(F(4))) + F(7)) × 5!)
- 57477 := ((5! + F(7)) + ((F(F(4)))^{F(7)}) × 7)
- 57479 := ((((-5) + F(7))! - F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(7))! / (-9!)))
- 57480 := 5! × (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 0
- 57481 := 5! × (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 1
- 57482 := 5! × (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 2
- 57483 := 5! × (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 3
- 57484 := 5! × (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 4

$$57485 := 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 5$$

$$57486 := 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 6$$

$$57487 := 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 7$$

$$57488 := 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 8$$

$$57489 := 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 8) + 9$$

$$57492 := (((5 + 7) + 4!) \times F((F(9)/2)))$$

$$57493 := (-((5! - F(7))) - (((F(4)!)! / 9) \times (-3!)))$$

$$57495 := ((-(5! \times F(7))) + (F(4)!) + (9^5))$$

$$57496 := (-5! - (F(7) \times ((F(4)! / (-9)) + (6!))))$$

$$57543 := (-(57) + ((5! \times F(F(4)))^{F(3)}))$$

$$57544 := ((-(5!) - (F(F(7)) \times (-5! + (4)))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$57546 := (((5 \times F(F(7))) \times (5! / F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$57554 := ((5! + F((F(7) + (5 + 5)))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$57587 := (((5! \times F((7 + 5))) + 8!) - F(7))$$

$$57604 := (((5! \times ((F(7) - F(6)))!) + 0!) \times 4)$$

$$57605 := (5 + ((7! / F(F(6)))^{F(-0!+5)}))$$

$$57624 := (((57 - F(6))^2) \times 4!)$$

$$57626 := (5 + (((7! / F(F(6)))^2) + F(F(6))))$$

$$57629 := (-5 + (((7! / F(F(6)))^2) + F(9)))$$

$$57635 := (-5) \times (-7 - (6! \times (F(F(3!)) - (5))))$$

$$57639 := (5 + (((7! / F(F(6)))^{F(3)} + F(9)))$$

$$57642 := (((5 \times (7! + 6!)) + F(F((F(4)!))) \times 2)$$

$$57646 := (((5! + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4!) - F(F(6))))$$

$$57647 := ((-5) \times (-((7! / F(6))) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$57664 := (-5!) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (6! / F(4))))$$

$$57665 := (-5) \times (-F(7) + (-6! \times (F(F(6)) - (5))))$$

$$57674 := (((5! + (7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(7)) + F(4!)))$$

$$57680 := ((F(-(5 - 7))) + (6!)) \times 80$$

$$57684 := (((5! \times ((F(7) - F(6)))!) + (F(8))) \times 4)$$

$$57720 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 0$$

$$57721 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 1$$

$$57722 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 2$$

$$57723 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 3$$

$$57724 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 4$$

$$57725 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 5$$

$$57726 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 6$$

$$57727 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 7$$

$$57728 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 8$$

$$57729 := 5! + (7 + F(F(7)))^2 + 9$$

$$57732 := (((5^7) - F(F(7))) - ((F(3!)!)/2))$$

$$57733 := ((5! + F(7)) + ((7!/F(F(3!)))^{F(3)}))$$

$$57735 := (((5 \times 7!) - F(F(7))) + (F(3!)^5))$$

$$57736 := (-5! + ((F(F(7)) - 7) \times (F(3)^{F(6)})))$$

$$57742 := (((5! + 7) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(4!)!) \times 2))$$

$$57743 := (-((5! - 7)) \times ((F(F(7)) - 4!) - 3!))$$

$$57744 := (((5! \times F(7)) \times (F(7) + 4!)) + 4!)$$

$$57746 := (((5 \times F(7)) \times (((7 - 4)!)!) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$57754 := ((-5) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7)))) + (5 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))$$

$$57765 := (((5! \times (-7)) + F(F(7))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)$$

$$57769 := (((5! + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7))) - (6! \times F(9)))$$

$$57774 := (((-5!) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7))) + (7!) \times (F(4)!)$$

$$57793 := (((-5) - F(F(7))) + F((F(7) + 9))) + (F(3!)!)$$

$$57803 := (((5 - F(F(7))) + F((F(8) + 0!))) + (F(3!)!))$$

$$57813 := ((-((5! \times F(7))) - F((F(8) + 1))) \times (-3))$$

$$57827 := ((5! \times ((F(F(7)) + 8) \times 2)) - F(7))$$

$$57834 := (((5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8)) - 3) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$57835 := (-5) + ((F(F(7)) + 8) \times (F(3) \times 5!))$$

$$57840 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 0$$

$$57841 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 1$$

$$57842 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 2$$

$$57843 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 3$$

$$57844 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 4$$

$$57845 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 5$$

$$57846 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 6$$

$$57847 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 7$$

$$57848 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 8$$

$$57849 := 5! \times (F(F(7)) + 8) \times F(F(4)) + 9$$

$$57856 := ((5! - (7)) \times (8^{-5+F(6)}))$$

$$57866 := (-((5! + ((-7) \times 8!)/6))) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$57867 := ((-5) \times ((7!/(-8)) - F(F(F(6)))))) - F(7)$$

$$57880 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 0$$

$$57881 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 1$$

$$57882 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 2$$

$$57883 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 3$$

$$57884 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 4$$

$$57885 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 5$$

$$57886 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 6$$

$$57887 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 7$$

$$57888 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 8$$

$$57889 := 5 \times (7!/8 + F(F(8))) + 9$$

$$57896 := -((F((5 + F(7))) + ((8! \times (-9))/6)))$$

$$57897 := (-5!) + (((7!/F(8)) + 9) \times F(F(7)))$$

$$57934 := (((5! \times 7) \times F(9)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (F((F(4))!))!$$

$$57938 := (-5!) + (F(7) \times ((-9) \times (3!)!) + F(F(8))))$$

$$57947 := (((5 \times F((F(7) - 9)!))/4) - F(7))$$

$$57966 := ((5 - F(F(7))) + ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(6))!))$$

$$57967 := (((((-5) + F(7))!)/9) - F(F(6))) \times F(7)$$

$$57982 := ((5^7) + ((F(9) - 8!)/2))$$

$$57997 := ((((-5) + F(7))! - F(9)) + F((9 + F(7))))$$

$$58024 := ((((-5) + F((F(8) + 0!))) - 2) + (F((F(4))!))!)$$

$$58026 := ((-5) + 8!) + F((0! + F((2 + 6))))$$

$$58028 := ((-5) + F((F(8) + 0!))) + (2 + 8!)$$

$$58030 := (((F((-((5 - 8))!))! - 0!) + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!)))$$

$$58031 := ((F((-((5 - 8))!))! + F((0! + F(F(((3 \times 1)!))))))$$

$$58032 := (((F((-((5 - 8))!))! + 0!) + F((F(F(3!)) + F(2))))$$

$$58033 := (((5 + F((F(8) + 0!))) - 3) + (F(3))!)$$

$$58034 := ((((-5) + F((F(8) + 0!))) + (F(3))!) + F((F(4))!))$$

$$58036 := ((5 + F((F(8) + 0!))) + ((F(3) + (6))!))$$

$$58038 := ((5 + F((F(8) + 0!))) + (F(3) + 8!))$$

$$58044 := (((5 + F((F(8) + 0!))) + F((F(4)!)) + (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$58046 := (((5!/8) + F((0! + F(F((F(4)!)))))) + (F(6)!))$$

$$58080 := ((5! \times (F(8) + 0!)) \times (F(8) + 0!))$$

$$58136 := (((5 \times F(8)) + F((1 + F(F(3!)))))) + (F(6)!)$$

$$58143 := (((5! + F((F(8) + 1))) - F((F(4)!)) + (F(3)!))!$$

$$58148 := ((5! + F((F(8) + 1))) - ((F(4) - 8!)))$$

$$58151 := ((5! + F((F(8) + 1))) + (F((5 + 1)))!)$$

$$58154 := (((5! + F(F(8))) + (((1 + 5)!)) + F(4!))$$

$$58156 := (((5! + F((F(8) + 1))) + (5)) + (F(6)!))$$

$$58163 := (5 + (81 \times (6! - F(3))))$$

$$58189 := ((-5) - 8!) + ((-1) \times F(F(8))) \times (-9))$$

$$58193 := -((((F((-((5 - 8)!))! + 1) - (9 \times F(F(F(3!))))))$$

$$58194 := ((F(F((-5) + F((8 - 1)))) \times 9) - (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$58198 := (-5) - (((F(F(8)) + 1) \times (-9)) + 8!)$$

$$58199 := ((5 - 8!) + (F(F(-(1 - 9))) \times 9))$$

$$58233 := -((5 - 8^2)) \times F((F(3) \times F(3)))$$

$$58264 := (-5!) + (82 \times (6! - F((F(4)!))))$$

$$58274 := (((5! \times 8) + F(F((F(2) + (7)))))) + F(4!))$$

$$58296 := (5! - (((F(F(8)) - 2) \times (-9)) + (F(6)!))$$

$$58304 := ((5 \times ((F(F(8)) + 3!!) - 0!)) - F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$58305 := (((-5) + F(F(8))) + 3!!) \times 05$$

$$58308 := ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!!)) - (0! + F(8)))$$

$$58309 := ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!!)) - F(-(0! - 9)))$$

$$58314 := ((5! + (F(F(8)) \times (F(3!) + 1))) - (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$58315 := (-5) \times (F((F(8) + F(3))) - (F((1 + 5)!)))$$

$$58317 := ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!!)) - F((1 \times 7)))$$

$$58320 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 0$$

$$58321 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 1$$

$$58322 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 2$$

$$58323 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 3$$

$$58324 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 4$$

$$58325 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 5$$

$$58326 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 6$$

$$58327 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 7$$

$$58328 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 8$$

$$58329 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!! - 2) + 9$$

$$58330 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 0$$

$$58331 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 1$$

$$58332 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 2$$

$$58333 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 3$$

$$58334 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 4$$

$$58335 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 5$$

$$58336 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 6$$

$$58337 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 7$$

$$58338 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 8$$

$$58339 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + (3 + 3)!) + 9$$

$$58340 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 0$$

$$58341 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 1$$

$$58342 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 2$$

$$58343 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 3$$

$$58344 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 4$$

$$58345 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 5$$

$$58346 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 6$$

$$58347 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 7$$

$$58348 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 8$$

$$58349 := 5 \times (+F(F(8)) + 3!! + F(F(4))) + 9$$

$$58350 := (5 \times ((F(F(8)) + 3!!) + (5 - 0!)))$$

$$58351 := ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!!)) + F(F((5 + 1))))$$

$$58353 := (((5 + F(F(8))) + 3!!) \times 5) - F(3)$$

$$58354 := ((5 \times F(F(8))) + (((3!) \times 5) + (4!)))$$

$$58355 := (((5 + F(F(8))) + ((3! \times 5!))) \times 5)$$

$$58356 := (5 + (((F(F(8)) + 3!!) \times 5) + F(F(6))))$$

$$58359 := (-5) + (((F(F(8)) + 3!!) \times 5) + F(9))$$

$$58360 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 0$$

$$58361 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 1$$

$$58362 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 2$$

$$58363 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 3$$

$$58364 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 4$$

$$58365 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 5$$

$$58366 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 6$$

$$58367 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 7$$

$$58368 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 8$$

$$58369 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3! + 6!) + 9$$

$$58370 := (5 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(3!)) + ((7 - 0!)!))$$

$$58373 := ((5 \times ((F(F(8)) + 3!!) + 7)) + F(3!))$$

$$58374 := ((5 \times ((F(F(8)) + 3!!) + F(7))) - F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$58384 := (((5^8) - F(F(3))) - 8!)/(F(4)!)$$

$$58386 := ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!!)) + (8!/6!))$$

$$58396 := ((5 \times ((F(F(8)) + 3!!) + 9)) + F(F(6)))$$

$$58414 := (-5!) + (F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) \times 14)$$

$$58430 := (-5) \times (((-F(F(8))) - ((F(4))!)) - F(F(3!)) + 0!)$$

$$58433 := ((-5) \times ((-F(F(8))) - ((F(4))!)) - F(F(3!))) - F(3)$$

$$58434 := ((-5) \times ((-F(F(8))) - ((F(4))!)) - F(F(3!))) - F(F(F(4)))$$

$$58435 := (5! + (((F(F(8)) - F(4)) + 3!!) \times 5))$$

$$58437 := ((5 \times ((F(F(8)) + (4!)) + 3!!)) - F(7))$$

$$58439 := -((F((5!/8)) + (F(4) \times (-3^9))))$$

$$58440 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 0$$

$$58441 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 1$$

$$58442 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 2$$

$$58443 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 3$$

$$58444 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 4$$

$$58445 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 5$$

$$58446 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 6$$

$$58447 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 7$$

$$58448 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 8$$

$$58449 := 5! \times (-F(F(8) - F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!) + 9$$

$$58450 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 0$$

$$58451 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 1$$

$$58452 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 2$$

$$58453 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 3$$

$$58454 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 4$$

$$58455 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 5$$

$$58456 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 6$$

$$58457 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 7$$

$$58458 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 8$$

$$58459 := 5 \times (F(F(8)) + F(4)!) + 5! + 9$$

$$58464 := ((-5) + F((8 + F(4)))) \times (6! - 4!)$$

$$58465 := (5! + ((F(F(8)) + ((F(4) + 6!))) \times 5))$$

$$58466 := (((58 + F((F(4)!)) \times 6!) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$58469 := ((-5) \times ((-F(F(8))) - ((F(4)!))! - (F(F(6)))) + F(9))$$

$$58474 := ((-5) \times (-F(F(8))) - ((F(4)!))! + F((F(7) - F(F(F(4))))))$$

$$58478 := (((5! + (84)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$58494 := ((-5) \times ((-F(F(8))) - ((F(4)!))! - F(9)) - (F(4)!))$$

$$58495 := (5! - (((F(F(8)) + ((F(4)!))! + 9) \times (-5)))$$

$$58534 := ((5! \times (-((F(8) + 5!)) + 3!)) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))$$

$$58536 := (((5! - F(8)) \times 5!) + (3!^6))$$

$$58547 := ((5! \times (8 - (5! \times (-4)))) - F(7))$$

$$58560 := -((5! \times ((F((8 + 5)) - 6!) - 0!))$$

$$58563 := (F((5 + 8)) + (5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((3!)!)))$$

$$58564 := (((5! + 8) + 5!) - (6))^{F(F(4))}$$

$$58624 := (-5!) + (((F(F(8)) - (F(6)!)) \times (-2)) - 4)$$

$$58628 := ((-5!) - F(F(8))) - (((F(6)! \times (-2)) + F(F(8))))$$

$$58631 := (-((5! - 8!) - 6!)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1))$$

$$58632 := (-5!) + (((F(F(8)) - (F(6)!)) - F(3)) \times (-2))$$

$$58634 := (((-5!) + F(F(8))) + ((6! \times F(3))) + F(4!))$$

$$58636 := (-5!) - (((F(F(8)) - (F(6)!)) \times F(3)) - F(6))$$

$$58641 := ((F((5!/8)) + (F(6)!)) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 1)))$$

$$58643 := ((-5) \times F(8)) - ((-F(F(F(6)))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \times (-F(3)))$$

$$58644 := (((F((5!/8)) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4)!))! + F(4!))$$

$$58654 := (5! + ((8 + 6) \times F((-5) + 4!)))$$

$$58673 := ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + (6!))) + ((7^3)))$$

$$58706 := ((5! \times (F(8) + F((F(7) + 0!)))) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$58732 := (((5 - F(F(8))) - F(7)) + (F(3!)!)) \times 2$$

$$58734 := (((F((-((5-8)))!))! - 7) - F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$58743 := (-5) + ((-8!) + F((7 \times F(4)))) \times (-F(3))$$

$$58744 := (((5 - F(F(8))) - 7) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$58747 := (-5) + (8 \times ((7! + F(4!))/7))$$

$$58748 := (((-5) + F(8)) \times 7!) - (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8)))$$

$$58753 := (5 + ((F(F(8)) - ((F(7) - 5)!)) \times (-F(3))))$$

$$58754 := (((-5!) + F(F(8))) + (F(7) \times 5!)) + F(4!)$$

$$58755 := (5 \times (F(F(8)) + (-7) \times (5 - 5!)))$$

$$58758 := ((5 + (F(8) \times (F(7) + 5!))) \times F(8))$$

$$58762 := (((F((-((5-8)))!))! - (-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 2)$$

$$58764 := ((((-5) - F(F(8))) + F(7)) + (F(6)!)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$58768 := (((5 \times 8!)/(-7)) + (F(6) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$58769 := ((F((5+8)) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(6)!)/(-9)))$$

$$58783 := (((5 \times F(F(8))) + 7!) - F((8 \times F(3))))$$

$$58784 := (((5 - F(F(8))) + (F(7) + 8!)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$58794 := (((5 \times F(8)) \times 7!)/9) - (F(4)!)$$

$$58795 := (((5 \times F(8)) \times 7!)/9) - (5)$$

$$58799 := ((((-5) \times F(8)) \times 7!) + 9)/(-9)$$

$$58834 := (((5 \times F(F(8))) + 8) + (F(3!)^4))$$

$$58836 := (-((5! \times F(8))) + ((F(F(8)) - 3!) \times 6))$$

$$58842 := ((F((-((5-8)))!))! + ((F(8)^{F(4)}) \times 2))$$

$$58844 := (5! - (((-8!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4))) + (4!))$$

$$58860 := (((5! \times (-8)) - F(8)) \times (-60))$$

$$58864 := (((58 - F(F(8))) + (F(6)!)) \times F(F(4))$$

$$58868 := (((5! - F(F(8))) - F(F(8))) + (F(6)!)) + 8!)$$

$$58884 := (5! + (((8! - F(F(8))) + 8) \times F(F(4))))$$

$$58937 := (-((5! - 8)) + (9^{-F(3)+7}))$$

$$58943 := (((-((5^8)) + 9!) + F(4!)) + (F(3)!))!$$

$$58945 := (((5 \times F(F(8))) + F(9)) + F((4! - 5)))$$

$$58950 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 0$$

$$58951 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 1$$

$$58952 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 2$$

$$58953 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 3$$

$$58954 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 4$$

$$58955 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 5$$

$$58956 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 6$$

$$58957 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 7$$

$$58958 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 8$$

$$58959 := -5! + F(8) + 9^5 + 9$$

$$58968 := ((5! + (8!/(9 + 6))) \times F(8))$$

$$58975 := (5 \times (F(F(8)) + (9 + (7 \times 5!))))$$

$$59033 := ((5 + (9^{-0!+3!})) - F(F(3!)))$$

$$59035 := (-((5 + 9)) + ((0! + F(3!))^5))$$

$$59036 := (-5) + ((9^{-0!+3!}) - F(6))$$

$$59043 := ((-5) + (9^{0!+4})) - F(F(3))$$

$$59045 := ((5 - 9) + ((0! + F((F(4)!))^5))$$

$$59046 := (5 + ((9^{0!+4}) - F(6)))$$

$$59049 := ((-((5 - 9)) - 0!) \times (F(4)^9))$$

$$59050 := (((F((F(-(5 - 9))))!) + 0!)^5) + 0!)$$

$$59067 := (5 + ((9^{-0!+6})) + F(7))$$

$$59135 := ((5! - F(9)) + ((1 + F(3!))^5))$$

$$59148 := ((5! + ((9^{1+4}))) - F(8))$$

$$59196 := (((5! \times (-9)) + F(F(-(1 - 9)))) \times 6)$$

$$59264 := (5! + ((F((F(9)/2)) \times F(6)) + F(4!)))$$

$$59274 := ((-5) - F((F(9)/2))) \times (-F(7) + 4!))$$

$$59280 := (5! \times ((9 \times F((2 + 8))) - 0!))$$

$$59290 := (((5! \times 9) - 2) \times F((9 + 0!)))$$

$$59306 := (((5 + F(9))^3) - F((0! + (6))))$$

$$59307 := (((5 + F(9))^3) + 0!) - F(7)$$

$$59309 := (((5 + F(9))^3) - 0!) - 9$$

$$59313 := (((5 + F(9))^3) - ((1 \times 3)!))$$

$$59320 := (((5 + F(9))^3) + ((2 \times 0)!))$$

$$59323 := (((5 + F(9))^3) - 2) + 3!$$

$$59332 := (((5 + F(9))^3) + F((3! + F(2))))$$

$$59333 := (((5 + F(9))^3) + 3!) + F(3!)$$

$$59334 := (((5 + F(9))^3) + F(F(3!))) - (F(4)!)$$

$$59335 := (((5 + F(9))^3) + F(F(3!))) - (5)$$

$$59336 := ((5! - F(9)) \times (3!)) - F((3 \times 6))$$

$$59337 := ((-5) + (-9!)/F(F(3!))) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-7))$$

$$59340 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 0$$

$$59341 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 1$$

$$59342 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 2$$

$$59343 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 3$$

$$59344 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 4$$

$$59345 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 5$$

$$59346 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 6$$

$$59347 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 7$$

$$59348 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 8$$

$$59349 := (5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(F(4!))) + 9$$

$$59355 := (-5) \times (9 + ((F(F(3!)) - 5!) \times 5!))$$

$$59364 := (((5 + F(9))^3 + F(F(6))) + (4!))$$

$$59373 := (-((5! - (9!/3!))) - F((F(7) + 3)))$$

$$59387 := (((5 \times ((9 + 3)!)/8!) - F(7))$$

$$59394 := (((5! \times (-9)) - 3!) + (9!/(F(4)!))$$

$$59400 := ((5! \times 9) \times F((F(F(4)! + (0! + 0!))))$$

$$59409 := (((-5!) \times F((F(9) - 4!))) - 0!) \times (-9)$$

$$59424 := ((-((5! \times F(9))) + (F(4!)/2)) + (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$59432 := (F(((5 + 9) + 4)) \times (F(F(3!)) + 2))$$

$$59445 := (((5 + F(9))^{F(4)} + (F(4)!)) + 5!)$$

$$59454 := (((5! \times 9) + F(F((F(4)!))) \times 54$$

$$59455 := (((5! \times 9) + F(F(F(4)))) \times 55$$

$$59467 := (-5) - ((-9) \times (F(4!) - (F(6)!)) - (7!))$$

$$59468 := (((F(-((5 - 9)))!)! + ((F(F(4)) \times ((F(6)! - F(F(8)))))))$$

$$59471 := (-F((-((5 - 9)))!) - ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-7!)) + 1))$$

$$59472 := (-F((-((5 - 9)))!) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-7! \times F(2))))$$

$$59473 := ((5! + F(9)) + ((F(4) \times F(7))^3))$$

$$59474 := (F(F(-((5 - 9)))) - ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times (-7!)) + F(4!)))$$

$$59476 := ((-((5 - 9)) - F(4!)) + (7! \times F(F(6))))$$

$$59478 := ((F(-((5 - 9)))! - (F(4!) - ((7! \times F(8))))$$

$$59484 := (((-((5! + 9)) \times F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4)!))$$

$$59485 := (-5) \times ((9 - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (-8) \times 5!))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59488 &:= (-5) + ((9!/(F(4)!) - F(8+8))) \\ 59490 &:= ((-59) + ((F(4)!)!) \times 90) \\ 59493 &:= -(F(-((5-9) \times 4)) - (9!/3!)) \\ 59520 &:= (5! \times ((9 \times F(5 \times 2)) + 0!)) \\ 59539 &:= (-((5! - (9^5))) + F((3! + 9))) \\ 59544 &:= (((-5) - F(9)) - (-5! \times F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 4!) \\ 59546 &:= ((5! + (9^5)) + F(((F(4)!) + F(6)))) \\ 59548 &:= (-((5 - (9^5))) + (4! \times F(8))) \\ 59614 &:= (((5+9) \times ((6+1)!) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\ 59634 &:= ((-((5! + (9!/(-6)))) - 3!!) - (F(4)!) \\ 59640 &:= (5! \times (((9!/6!) - (F(4)!) - 0!)) \\ 59641 &:= ((-((5! + (9!/(-6)))) - ((F(4)!)!) + 1) \\ 59642 &:= ((-((5! + (9!/(-6)))) - ((F(4)!)!) + 2) \\ 59643 &:= (-((5! + ((9!/(-6)) - F(4)))) - 3!!) \\ 59644 &:= (-((5! + ((9!/(-6)) - (4)))) - ((F(4)!)!) \\ 59645 &:= (((5 - (9!/(-6))) - ((F(4)!)!) - 5!) \\ 59646 &:= ((-((5! + (9!/(-6)))) + (F(4)!) - (6!)) \\ 59647 &:= ((-((5! + (9!/(-6)))) - ((F(4)!)!) + 7) \\ 59649 &:= ((-((5! + (9!/(-6)))) - ((F(4)!)!) + 9) \\ 59665 &:= ((F(((5-9)!) - F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\ 59687 &:= (5 - ((F(9) - 6!) \times 87)) \\ 59734 &:= ((5! - F(9)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(3)^{F(F(4)!)})) \\ 59747 &:= (5! + (((9! - 7!)/(F(4)!) - F(7))) \\ 59754 &:= (((-((5! - F(9))) \times F(F(7))) + 5!) \times (-F(4))) \\ 59756 &:= ((-((5+9)) + 7!) - (-5 \times F(F(F(6)))) \\ \\ 59770 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 0 \\ 59771 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 1 \\ 59772 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 2 \\ 59773 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 3 \\ 59774 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 4 \\ 59775 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 5 \\ 59776 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 6 \\ 59777 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 7 \\ 59778 &:= 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$59779 := 5 \times (F(F(9) - F(7))) + 7! + 9$$

$$59784 := -((5! + ((-9) \times F(7)) \times (8^{F(4)})))$$

$$59785 := (5! + ((F((9 + 7)) + F(F(8))) \times 5))$$

$$59794 := ((5! + F(9)) + (-((7! - 9!)/(F(4)!)))$$

$$59835 := (-5) \times ((-F(9) - F(F(8))) - F((F(F(3!)) - (5))))$$

$$59849 := -(((5! + F(9)) - 8!) - (F(4)^9))$$

$$59864 := (((5! + F(9)) - (F(8) \times 6!)) \times (-4))$$

$$59943 := (-F((5 + 9))) \times (9 - (F((F(4)!)) \times F(F(3!))))$$

$$59944 := (59 \times (-((F(9)^{F(4)})) + (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$59969 := (((F(-(5 - 9)))^9) + (F(6)!)) - F(9))$$

$$59976 := (((5! \times 9) - 9) \times 7) \times F(6)$$

$$59994 := (((F(-(5 - 9)))^9) - 9) + (F((F(4)!))!))$$

$$60247 := (((F(6) + 0!)!/(2 + 4)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$60264 := (((F(6) + 0!)^2) \times (6! + 4!))$$

$$60276 := ((F((F(6) + 0!)) + (-2) \times 7!) \times (-6))$$

$$60333 := (((6! + F(F((0! + 3!)))) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(3)!))$$

$$60334 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (((-((0! - 3!))! - F(F(3!))) \times ((F(4)!))!)))$$

$$60335 := -(((F(F(F(6))) - 0!) + ((3!)! \times (F(F(3!)) - 5))))$$

$$60336 := (((F(6) + 0!)! / 3!) - F((F(3) \times 6)))$$

$$60344 := ((-F((F(6) + 0!))) + (F(F(3!)) \times ((F(4)!))!)) \times 4$$

$$60347 := (((((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!)/F(4)!)) - F(7))$$

$$60348 := (6 \times (-0!) + (((F(3!)! / 4) - (F(8))))$$

$$60354 := (F(F(6)) \times ((0 - 3!) + (5! \times 4!)))$$

$$60355 := (((F(6) + 0!)! / 3!) + (-5 - 5!))$$

$$60360 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 0$$

$$60361 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 1$$

$$60362 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 2$$

$$60363 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 3$$

$$60364 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 4$$

$$60365 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 5$$

$$60366 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 6$$

$$60367 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 7$$

$$60368 := ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!) / 6 + 8$$

$$\begin{aligned} 60369 &:= ((F(6) + 0!)! - 3!)/6 + 9 \\ 60372 &:= (6 \times (((-0!) - F(3!)) + (7!)) \times 2) \\ 60376 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / 3!) - (F(7) \times F(6))) \\ 60378 &:= (-(6) \times (0! - (F(3) \times (7! - 8)))) \\ 60384 &:= ((-F(6)) + ((0! + 3!)!) \times (8 + 4)) \\ 60390 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / 3!) - (90)) \\ 60394 &:= (F((F(6) + 0!)) - (((3!)! - 9!) / (F(4)!))) \\ 60396 &:= (((6! - 0!) \times 3) \times (F(9) - (6))) \\ 60399 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / 3!) - ((9 \times 9))) \\ 60425 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - F((2 \times 5))) \\ 60432 &:= (((F(6) - 0!)! - 4) \times (3! \times 2)) \\ 60435 &:= ((F(6) + 0!) \times (((F((F(4)!))! / 3!) - (5))) \\ 60438 &:= (((6! - 0!) \times 4) + F(3)) \times F(8) \\ 60440 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - 40) \\ 60444 &:= (((F(6) - 0!)! - F(4)) \times (F(4) \times 4)) \\ 60446 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - F((F(4) + (6)))) \\ 60447 &:= (((F(6)! - 0!) + (-4) \times (F((F(4)!)) - (7!)))) \\ 60448 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - (4 \times 8)) \\ 60449 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) + ((F(4) - F(9)))) \\ 60453 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-0! - (4! \times 5!))) - 3!) \\ 60454 &:= (((((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - (5)) - F(F((F(4)!)))) \\ 60455 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - (5 \times 5)) \\ 60456 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! - (4! + 5!)) / 6) \\ 60458 &:= -((F(F(6)) + ((0! - ((4! \times 5!) \times F(8)))))) \\ 60459 &:= (-(F(F(6))) \times (0! - (((F(4)!))! \times (-5 - 9)))) \\ 60460 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-0! + (-4) \times 6!)) + 0!) \\ 60462 &:= ((F(6) + 0!) \times (((F((F(4)!))! / 6) - 2)) \\ 60463 &:= ((F((F(6) + 0!)) + (-F(4)) \times (F(6)!)) / (-F(3))) \\ 60464 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) + (F(6) - 4!)) \\ 60466 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! / (F(4)!)) - (F(6) + (6))) \\ 60467 &:= (((60 + 4!) \times 6!) - F(7)) \\ 60468 &:= (((((F(6) + 0!)! - (4!)) / 6) - 8) \\ 60472 &:= -((F(6) + (((04!) \times 7!) / (-2))) \\ 60474 &:= (-(6) - (((0 - F(4)) \times 7!) \times 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}60475 &:= (((F(6) + 04) \times 7!) - (5)) \\60476 &:= (((((F(6) + 0!))! - (-((F(4) - (7))))))! / 6) \\60477 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (0! - (4 \times 7!))) / (-7)) \\60478 &:= ((6 \times (0! + (F(F(4)) \times 7!))) - 8) \\60479 &:= (((((F(6) + 0!))! / (F(4))!) - F(-((7 - 9)))) \\ \\60480 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 0 \\60481 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 1 \\60482 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 2 \\60483 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 3 \\60484 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 4 \\60485 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 5 \\60486 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 6 \\60487 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 7 \\60488 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 8 \\60489 &:= 6! \times 04 \times F(8) + 9 \\ \\60490 &:= (((((F(6))! - 0!) - F(4!)) \times (-9 - 0!)) \\60492 &:= (6 \times ((-0!) - (-((F(F(4)) - 9))))! \times (-2)) \\60493 &:= ((F(6) + 0!) + ((4! + 9!) / 3!)) \\60494 &:= (((60 + 4!) + 9!) / (F(4))!) \\60496 &:= -(((F(6) - (04)!) + (9! / (-6)))) \\60504 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (05)!) + 0!) \times 4!) \\60536 &:= (((((F(6) + 0!))! \times (-5!)) - (F(3!))!) / (-6!)) \\60543 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((05)! \times 4!) + 3)) \\60544 &:= (((F(6))! \times (0 - 5)) + (F((F(4))!)^{F(4)!})) \\60549 &:= (((((F(6))! - 0!) \times (-5)) + (4^9)) \\60564 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((0 \times 5)!) + 6!) \times 4) \\60576 &:= ((60/5) \times (7! + F(6))) \\60594 &:= (-6 + (((0! + 5))! + 9!) / (F(4))!) \\60614 &:= (((F(6))! - 0!) - (F((F(F(6)) - 1)) \times (-F(4)))) \\60615 &:= ((F(6))! - (F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-F(-((1 - 5)))))) \\60625 &:= (((F(F(6)) - 0!) \times (-6!)) + F(25)) \\60630 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 0!) \times 6) - ((3! + 0!)!) \\60633 &:= (((-6) - F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-3)) + (F(3!))!\end{aligned}$$

- 60634 := $(-(((F(6) - 0!)!) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) - F(F(4))))$
- 60636 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 06) - ((F(F(3)) + 6)!))$
- 60637 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 06) + (F(F(3)) - (7!)))$
- 60642 := $((((F(F(F(6))) + 0!) \times 6) - (((F(4))! + F(2))))!$
- 60643 := $((-(F(F(6))) \times F(F((0! + (6)))))) + (4^{F(3!)})$
- 60644 := $(-(((F(6) - 0!)!) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) + F((F(4))!)))$
- 60648 := $((F(6) - ((0 - 6!) \times 4)) \times F(8))$
- 60649 := $((F(6))! + ((F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times F(4)) + F(9))$
- 60654 := $(6 \times (-0!) + (((F(6))! + 5!)/4))$
- 60669 := $(((((F(6))!/06) + F(F(6))) \times 9)$
- 60678 := $-((((F(6) - 0!)! - (6 \times (7 + F(F(8))))))$
- 60679 := $(((((F(6) + 0!)!/6) + F(F(7))) - F(9))$
- 60684 := $(6 \times (F((0! + F(6))) - (8!/(-4))))$
- 60692 := $((((F(6) + 0!) - F(-(F(6) - F(9)))))/(-2))$
- 60693 := $((((F(F(6)) - F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-9)) - 3)$
- 60694 := $((((F(F(6)) - F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-9)) - F(F(4)))$
- 60696 := $((F(F(6)) - F((-0!) + F(F(6)))) \times (-9!)/(F(6))!)$
- 60732 := $((((F(F(6)) \times (-0!)) - (7!)) \times (3! \times (-2)))$
- 60744 := $((F(F(6)) + (0! + 7!)) \times (F(4) \times 4))$
- 60747 := $-((F(F(6)) + (((0! - F(7)) \times (4! + 7!))))$
- 60769 := $((F(F((F(6) - 0!))) \times F(F(7))) + (6! \times 9))$
- 60774 := $(6 - ((0! - F(7)) \times (7! + 4!)))$
- 60783 := $((((F(F(6)) \times (-0!)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(F(8)) \times 3!))$
- 60813 := $((F(6) + 0!) \times (F((F(8) - 1)) - F(3!)))$
- 60831 := $((-(6) + F(-(0! - F(8)))) \times (F(3!) + 1))$
- 60837 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (F(-(0! - F(8))))/3) \times 7)$
- 60839 := $(F(6) + ((F(-(0! - F(8)))) - 3!) \times 9)$
- 60849 := $((F((F(F(6)) + 0!)) - (F(F(8)) + 4)) \times 9)$
- 60864 := $(-(F(F(6))) + (F(-(0! - F(8)))) \times (6 + F(4)))$
- 60873 := $(((((F(6))! + 0!) - (F(F(8)) \times (-F(7))))/3)$
- 60877 := $(-F(6) - (-((0! + 8)) \times F((F(7) + (7))))$
- 60879 := $(-(6) + (F(-(0! - 8) - F(7))) \times 9)$
- 60885 := $((F(6) + 0!) \times F((F(8) - F(F((8 - 5))))))$
- 60890 := $(6 + ((F(-(0! - F(8)))) \times 9) - 0!)$
- 60891 := $(6 + (F(-(0! - F(8)))) \times (9 \times 1))$

- 60892 := (6 - ((F(-((0! - F(8)))) × (-9)) - F(2)))
- 60893 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F((0! + F(8)))) × (-9)) + F(3!))
- 60894 := (6 + ((F(-((0! - F(8)))) × 9) + F(4)))
- 60898 := (F(F(6)) - ((F(-((0! - F(8)))) × (-9)) + 8))
- 60906 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 0!)) × 9) + F(F(06)))
- 60906 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 0!)) × 9) + F(F(06)))
- 60919 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 0!)) × 9) + F((1 × 9)))
- 60928 := (((-6) - 0!) × F(9)) × (-2⁸))
- 60933 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 0!)) × 9) + (3! × F(3!)))
- 60939 := ((6 + F((0! + 9) × F(3))) × 9)
- 60944 := (((F((F(6) - 0!))! / 9!) + (4 × F(F(F((F(4)!))))))
- 60948 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 0!)) × 9) + (F(4) × F(8)))
- 60965 := (((6! - 0!) - F(9)) × F((6 + 5)))
- 60967 := ((6! - ((09)! / (-6))) - F(F(7)))
- 60974 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 0!)) × 9) + F((7 + 4)))
- 60992 := ((F(6))! - ((0! - 9) × F((9 × 2))))
- 60993 := (((6! - 0!) + F(9)) × (9^{F(3)}))
- 61057 := ((F(6))! + (F((F(10)/5)) × F(F(7))))
- 61225 := ((F(6))! - (F((F(F(((1 + 2)!)) - 2)) × (-5)))
- 61274 := (((6¹⁺²) × F(F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
- 61278 := (-6) × (((((1 + 2)!)! + F(7)) - F(F(8))))
- 61284 := ((-((6! + 12)) + F(F(8))) × (F(4))!)
- 61334 := (-((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (((3!)! - F(F(F(3!)))) × (-F(4)!)))
- 61336 := (-((F(F(6)) - 1)) - (3! × ((3!)! - F(F(F(6))))))
- 61337 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (-1 - 3!)) × 3!) - F(7))
- 61338 := (6 × (((-1) × (3!)! - 3) + F(F(8))))
- 61343 := (-F((6 + 1))) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - (((F(4)!)!)) × 3!))
- 61344 := ((F(F(F(6))) - ((-1 + 3!) + F(4))) × (F(4))!)
- 61345 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (-1 - 3!)) × (F(4))! - (5))
- 61346 := (F(F(F(6))) - (((1 + 3!)! × (-4 + 6)))
- 61347 := (F(F(F(6))) - (-1 - ((3! + (4)) × 7!)))
- 61348 := (((F(F(F(6))) × (-1)) + ((3!)!) × (-F(4)!)) - 8)
- 61350 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (-1 - 3!)) × (5 + 0!))
- 61356 := ((-6!) + F(F(((1 × 3) + 5))) × 6)
- 61361 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (1 - 3!)) × 6) - 1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 61362 &:= (6 \times ((1 - 3!!) + F(F((6 + 2)))))) \\
 61363 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (1 - 3!!)) \times 6) + F(F(3))) \\
 61364 &:= (((((F(F(F(6))) \times (-1)) + ((3!)!) \times (-6)) + F((F(4)!))) \\
 61368 &:= (6 \times ((F((1 \times 3)) - 6!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 61383 &:= (F(F(6)) + (((-1 + 3!!) - F(F(8))) \times (-3!))) \\
 61386 &:= ((-(((6! + 1) - 3!)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 61394 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - ((((-1 + 3!)! \times (-F(9))) - F(4!))) \\
 61398 &:= (6 \times (1 - ((F(F(3!)) \times F(9)) - F(F(8)))))) \\
 61434 &:= (-6) + (((1 + 4)!) \times (F(3!)^{F(4)})) \\
 61435 &:= (-((6 - 1)) + ((F((F(4)!))^3) \times 5!)) \\
 \\
 61440 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 0 \\
 61441 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 1 \\
 61442 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 2 \\
 61443 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 3 \\
 61444 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 4 \\
 61445 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 5 \\
 61446 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 6 \\
 61447 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 7 \\
 61448 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 8 \\
 61449 &:= (6 - 1)! \times F(F(4)!)^{F(4)} + 9 \\
 \\
 61463 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(3!)))) \\
 61465 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - 1)) - ((-((F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5))) \\
 61466 &:= -((((F(F(6)) + 1) - F(4!)) + (-6!) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 61468 &:= -((((F(F(6)) - 1) - F(4!)) - (6! \times F(8))) \\
 61474 &:= ((-F(F(6))) \times (1 - ((F(4)!)!)) - (-7 - F(4!))) \\
 61483 &:= ((-((6 - 1)) + F(4!)) - (-F(8) \times (3!)!)) \\
 61494 &:= ((6 + F(((1 \times 4)!)!)) + ((9!/4!))) \\
 61495 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) + (4 \times F(F(F((F((9 - 5)!)!)))))) \\
 61512 &:= (F(F((6 + 1))) \times (5! + F(12))) \\
 61596 &:= (((((F(6) + 1)!/5) - F(9)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 61630 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) + (((1 + F(6))!)/(-3! - 0!)))) \\
 61631 &:= ((61 \times 6!) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 61634** := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((1 \times 6)!) \times 3!) + F(4!))$
61654 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - (((1 + F(6)))! / 5) + (4!)))$
61739 := $((F(6)!) - 1) - ((7! / F(3!)) \times (-F(9)))$
61744 := $((F((F(6) + 1)) \times (F(F(7)) - (F(4)!) \times F((F(4)!)))$
61746 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (-1) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))) + (F(6)!)$
61748 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (1 - F(F(7)))) \times F(F(4))) + 8!$
61755 := $((F((F(F(6)) - 1)) \times 7) + (5! \times 5!))$
61774 := $((F((F(F(6)) - 1)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(7)))) + ((F(4)!)!)$
61776 := $((F((6 + 1)))! / (-7! + (7! \times F(F(6))))$
61794 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((1 + 7)!) / 9) + F(4!))$
61834 := $((6! - 1) \times (83 + F(4)))$
61844 := $((F(F(6)) - 1) - ((-8) \times F(4)) / (F(4)!))$
61846 := $((F(F(6)) + 1) + ((-8) \times F(4)) / (-6))$
61864 := $-((F(6) - ((F(18) - (6)) \times 4!))$
61920 := $((((6 - 1))! - F(9)) \times (((2 + 0!)!)!)$
61944 := $((F((F(6) + (1 + 9))) - F(4)) \times 4!)$
61954 := $(F((F(6) + 1)) - ((F(9) - 5!) \times ((F(4)!)!))$
61974 := $((F(F(6)) + 1) \times ((9 \times F(F(7))) + ((F(4)!)!))$
61994 := $-((F(F(6)) - (-1 + (F((9 + 9)) \times 4!)))$
62024 := $(F(6) + (F((20 - 2)) \times 4!))$
62033 := $((F(F(F(6))) + F(2)) \times F((0! + F(3)))) / 3!$
62034 := $((-F((F(6) \times 2))) \times (-0! - F(F(3)))) + (F((F(4)!)!))$
62144 := $((F(6)!) + (2 \times (-F((1 + F((F(4)!)!)))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))))$
62164 := $((-((6! - 2)) \times (-1 - F(F(6)))) + F(4!))$
62168 := $((F(6)!) + (2 \times ((-1 - F(F(6))) + F(F(8))))$
62178 := $((F(6)!) - (2 \times (17 - F(F(8))))$
62184 := $((F(6) - F(2)) + F(18)) \times 4!$
62186 := $((F(6)!) + (2 \times (-F(-((1 - 8)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
62193 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 2) - 19) + (F(3)!)$
62194 := $((F(6)!) - (-((F(21) - 9)) \times F(F(4))))$
62196 := $((F(6)!) + (2 \times (F(F(-((1 - 9)))) - F(6))))$
62204 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 2) + (F(((2 + 0!)!)!)) - F((F(4)!)!))$
62206 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 2) - (((2 + 0!)! - (F(6)!)!))$
62210 := $((F(6)!) - (-2) \times (F(21) - 0!))$
62211 := $((F(6)!) - ((-2) \times F(21)) + 1)$

- 62212 := (((6 + 2))! - (F(21) × (-2)))
- 62213 := ((F(6))! + ((F(2) + (F(21) × F(3))))))
- 62214 := (((F(6))! - (-2) × F(21))) + F(F(4)))
- 62216 := (((F(F(F(6))) + 2) × 2) + (F((1 × 6)))!)
- 62218 := (6 + ((2 × F(21)) + 8!))
- 62224 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (F((2 + 2)))!) × 2) + (F((F(4))!)!))
- 62228 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(2 + 2)))!)) × 2) + 8!)
- 62233 := ((F(F(6)) - (-2) × F(F(2³))) + (F(3!)!))
- 62234 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(2)) × 2) + (F(3!)!) + (4!))
- 62236 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (((F(2) + 3))! + (F(6))!))
- 62237 := (((F(6))! - F(2)) - (-2) × (F(F(F(3!))) + F(7)))
- 62238 := ((F(6))! - (-2) × (F((F(2) + 3!)) + F(F(8))))
- 62246 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + F((F(2) + F((F(4))!)))) + (F(6))!)
- 62248 := ((6²) - ((-2) × F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 8!)
- 62254 := ((F(6))! + (2 × (F(F(F((F(2) + (5)))))) + F(F((F(4))!))))
- 62256 := (F(6) × (((F((2 + 2)))! ⁵) + 6))
- 62264 := ((F(6))! + (2 × ((2 + F(F(F(6)))) + (4!))))
- 62304 := (((F(F(F(6))) - 2) + ((F(3!) + 0!)!)) / (F(4))!)
- 62332 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (F(3!)!) + ((3 + 2))!))
- 62335 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (F(3!)!) + (3 + 5!))
- 62336 := (((-62) - F(F(F(3!)))) × (-F(3))) + (F(6))!)
- 62338 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (F(3!)!) + (3! × F(8)))
- 62343 := (F((F(6) × 2) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - (((F(4))!)!) × 3!))
- 62346 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(2) + 3!)! + F(4!)) - F(6)))
- 62347 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(2) + 3!)! + F(4!)) - 7))
- 62348 := (((-6) + ((F(2) + 3!)!) + F(4!)) + F(F(8)))
- 62353 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + F(F(3!))) + 5!) + (F(3!)!)
- 62354 := ((F(F((6 + 2))) + ((F(3) + (5)))!) + F(4!))
- 62356 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 2) - (((3!)! / (-5)) - (F(6))!))
- 62374 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(2)) + F(F(3!))) + (7! + F(4!)))
- 62377 := (((6! - F(2)) + (F(3)^{F(7)})) × 7)
- 62378 := (((F(6))! × (-2) + 3!!) - (-F(7) × F(F(8))))
- 62384 := (((F(F(6)) + F(2)) × ((3!)! + 8)) + F(4!))
- 62388 := ((F(6))! + (2 × (F(F(F(3!))) + 88)))
- 62389 := (((F(F(6)) - 2) - 3!!) × (-89))

- 62424 := (((F((F(6) + 2)) - 4)²) × 4!)
- 62433 := (((F((F(6) × 2) + 4) × 3) × F(F(3!)))
- 62437 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) - F((F(4)!)) + (F(3!)!) + F(F(7)))
- 62445 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (F((F(4)!))!) + F(F((F(F(4) + (5))))))
- 62447 := (F((F(F(6) + F(2))) + (F((F(4)!)) × (4! × F(F(7)))))
- 62448 := (-(6!) + ((2^{F(4)!}) × F((4! - 8))))
- 62450 := ((F(6))! - (-2) × (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((5! - 0!))))
- 62451 := ((F(6))! - ((-2) × (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 5!) + 1))
- 62452 := ((F(6))! - ((F(F((2 × 4))) + 5!) × (-2)))
- 62453 := (((F(6))! + F(2)) - (F(F(4)) × (-5!) - F(F(F(3!))))))
- 62454 := (F(F(6)) × (-2) + ((4 + 5!) × 4!))
- 62456 := ((F(6))! + (2 × ((F(F(4) + 5!) + F(F(F(6))))))
- 62457 := ((F(F(6))²) + (4! × F((5 + F(7)))))
- 62458 := ((F(((6 - 2)!)) / (F(4)!)) - (-5) × F(F(8)))
- 62464 := (((6 - F(2))!) + F(F(4))) × (F(6)^{F(4)})
- 62466 := -(((6! - 2) × ((4! - 6!) / F(6)))
- 62468 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (((F(F(4))^{F(6)}) + 8!))
- 62473 := F(F(F(6))) - 2 + (F(4)! - F(F(7)))^{F(3)}
- 62474 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(2) + 4))! + (7!) + F(4!)))
- 62475 := (F(F(F(6))) - ((-F(2)) - F(4!)) - (7! + 5!))
- 62479 := (((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(F(7)) + F(9))))
- 62482 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 2) + (((F(4)!)) × F((F(8) - F(2)))))
- 62487 := (F(F(6)) + ((-2) + ((F(4)!))!) × 87))
- 62493 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (-F(2)) - (-((F(4) × F(9))) × (3!)!))
- 62494 := (-F(F((6 + 2))) + (((F(4)!))! × (F(9) × F(4))))
- 62496 := ((62 × 4!) × (F(9) + F(6)))
- 62497 := (F((F(F(6) + 2)) + ((F(4)!))! × (F(9) + F(7))))
- 62534 := (F((F(6) + F(2))) - ((5^{3!}) × (-4)))
- 62538 := (F(F(6)) × (((-2) + 5!)^{F(3)}) - F(F(8)))
- 62542 := ((F(F(6)) + (2 × (5^{F(4)!}))) × 2)
- 62543 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(2)) × 5!) + F(4)) / F(F(3!)))
- 62544 := (6! - ((-((2⁵)) × F(4!)) / 4!))
- 62547 := (((F(F(F(6))) + 2) × 5!) / F(F((F(4)!))) - F(7))
- 62548 := (((6 × 2) + (-5!) × F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) / (-F(8))

$$62560 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 0$$

$$62561 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 1$$

$$62562 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 2$$

$$62563 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 3$$

$$62564 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 4$$

$$62565 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 5$$

$$62566 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 6$$

$$62567 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 7$$

$$62568 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 8$$

$$62569 := (F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5! / F(F(6)) + 9$$

$$62584 := (((F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times 5!) / F(8)) + (4!))$$

$$62604 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (2^{F(6)+0!})) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$62634 := (((F(6))! / (-2)) - (6! - F(3))) \times (-F(4))$$

$$62635 := (((((F(6))! / 2) + (6!)) \times 3) - (5))$$

$$62639 := ((F(6))! - ((F(2) - (6! \times (-3) + F(9))))))$$

$$62640 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 0$$

$$62641 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 1$$

$$62642 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 2$$

$$62643 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 3$$

$$62644 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 4$$

$$62645 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 5$$

$$62646 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 6$$

$$62647 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 7$$

$$62648 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 8$$

$$62649 := 6! \times (-2 + F(F(6) + F(4))) + 9$$

$$62656 := (((F(6) \times (-2)) + 6!) \times F((5 + 6)))$$

$$62664 := (F(F(6)) \times ((26 + 6!) \times 4))$$

$$62674 := ((F(6))! + (((-2) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))))$$

$$62678 := ((F(6))! + (2 \times (F((6 + 7)) + F(F(8)))))$$

$$62694 := (((F(F(6)))^2 + (6!)) \times 9) \times (F(4))!$$

$$62723 := ((F((F(F(6)) - 2)) \times (F(7) + 2)) + F(3!))$$

$$62736 := (((6! - (2^{F(7)})) \times (-3)) + (F(6))!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62737 &:= (- (6!) + (F((-2) + F(7))) \times ((3!)! - 7)) \\ 62744 &:= (- (F(6)) + (((2^{F(7)}) \times F(F(4))) + F(4!))) \\ 62745 &:= (((6! - 2) - F(7)) \times F(((F(4))! + (5)))) \\ 62746 &:= (((6 - 2)^7) + F(4!)) - 6 \\ 62748 &:= (((6! + (27)) \times 4) \times F(8)) \\ 62752 &:= (((6 - 2)^7) + F((5 - F(2))!)) \\ 62755 &:= ((F(F(F(6)) + F(2))) - (7! + 5!)) \times 5 \\ 62766 &:= (((6! - 2) + F(F(7))) \times 66) \\ 62773 &:= (((((F(6) + F(2)))! / 7) - F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\ 62777 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (F(2) + 7!)) - F(F(7))) \times F(7)) \\ 62778 &:= (- ((F(6) + ((2 + 7)! / (-7)))) + F(F(8))) \\ 62783 &:= (((((F(6) + F(2)))! / 7) + F(F(8))) - 3) \\ 62786 &:= (((((F(6))! \times (-2)) / (-7)) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!) \\ 62797 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((-2) + F(7)) - (9! / (-7))) \\ 62814 &:= (- ((6! + 2) \times (-81) - (F(4))!) \\ 62838 &:= (6! - (2 \times ((F(8)^3) - 8!)) \\ 62873 &:= (F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) + (87 \times (3!)!)) \\ 62894 &:= (((6! \times (2 + F(8))) - F(9)) + F(4!)) \\ 62898 &:= (6! - ((-2) \times F(F(8))) + (F(9) - 8!)) \\ 62929 &:= (((F(6))! \times 2) - F((F(9 - 2) + 9))) \\ 62932 &:= ((6! + (-((F(2) - 9))!)) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2))) \\ 62938 &:= (((F(6))! \times 2) + 9) - F((F(F(3)) + (F(8)))) \\ 62944 &:= (- ((F(6) + F((2 \times 9)))) + (4^{F(F(4)!)) \\ 62958 &:= ((F(6))! + ((-2) + (9 \times 5!)) \times F(8)) \\ 62963 &:= (((F(6))! \times 2) + F(9)) - F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \\ 62966 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 2) + ((F(9) + 6!) + (F(6))!)) \\ 62985 &:= ((6! + F(-((F(2) - 9)))) \times 85) \\ 63036 &:= ((-(((F(F(6))^{F(3)} - 0!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 6) \\ 63038 &:= (((F(6) \times F((F(3!) + 0!)))^{F(3)} - F(F(8))) \\ 63047 &:= (((F(6))! + F((F(F(3!) + 0!))) - ((4! - 7!)) \\ 63063 &:= ((F(F(6))^{F(3)}) \times (-0! + F((6 \times F(3)))) \\ 63064 &:= (F((6 \times 3)) + (((0! + F(6))! / (F(4))!)) \\ 63070 &:= (((F(6))! + F((F(F(3)) + 0!))) + (7! - 0!)) \\ 63071 &:= (((F(6))! + F((F(F(3)) + 0!))) + ((7 \times 1)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 63072** := (((F(6))! + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!))) + ((7! + F(2))))
63073 := (((F(6))! + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!))) + (7! + F(3)))
63074 := (F(F(F(6))) - (((3!)! × (-0! + (7)))) - F(4!))
63079 := ((F(6) + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!))) - (7! × (-9)))
63086 := (-F((6 × 3))) + ((0! - F(F(8))) × (-6))
63088 := ((-6!) × F((F(3!) + 0!)) + (F(F(8)) × 8))
63092 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 3!) - F((09 × 2)))
63093 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 3!) - (-0! + F((9 × F(3))))))
63096 := ((F(6) × (F(F(F(3!))) + 0!)) - ((F(9) × 6!))
63127 := -(((F(6))! - (((3!)! × F(12)) - F(F(7))))))
63134 := -((F(F(F(6))) + (F(3!) × (1 - (F(F(3!))^{F(4)}))))))
63144 := (((F(F(6)) - 3!) × (-1 × 4!)) + F(4!))
63154 := -(((F(F(6)) - ((3! + 1)⁵))) - F(4!))
63156 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 3!) - (((1 × 5)!) × F(F(6))))
63160 := (F(6) × ((F(3!) × F(16)) - 0!))
63184 := ((6! - F(3)) × ((1 + F(8)) × 4))
63216 := -(((F(6))! + (F((3! × 2)) × (1 - 6!))))
63232 := ((F((F(6) × F(3))) + F(2)) × (F(3!)²))
63252 := ((F(6))! - ((F(F(3!))²) × (-52)))
63264 := ((F(6))! - (-32 × (6! - F(4))))
63265 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (((3!)! + F((2 × F(6)))))) × 5)
63272 := (F(6) × (((3!)! - F(2)) × (F(7) - 2)))
63273 := (F(F(6)) × ((F(3!) × F((2 × 7))) - 3))
63274 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 3!) - (F(2) + (7⁴)))
63279 := (F((F(6) + 3)) × ((-((F(2) - (7))))! - 9))
63294 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3!)!) + (2 × (-F(9) + F(4))))))
63296 := (((6! - F(3)) × (-2 + F(9))) + (F(6))!)
63315 := (-((F(F(6))³)) + (((F(3!) + 1)!) / 5))
63327 := (((F(6) × (3!)!) - 3) × (-2 + F(7)))
63328 := (((6! - F(F(3))) × 32) + 8!)
63333 := (((F(F(6)) × F(3!)) × F((3! + F(3)))) - 3)
63334 := (((F(F(6)) × F(3!)) × F((3! + F(3)))) - F(F(4)))
63336 := ((F(F(6)) × F(3!)) × F(((3 + 3) + F(6))))
63336 := ((F(F(6)) × F(3!)) × F(((3 + 3) + F(6))))
63338 := (((F(6) × (3!)!) - F(3)) × (3 + 8))

$$\begin{aligned}63339 &:= -((F(F(6)) - ((F(3!) \times (3!)!) \times (F(3) + 9)))) \\63344 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))) \times (3!)!) - 4) \times 4 \\63345 &:= (((F(6)^3) + 3) \times (F(4) + 5!)) \\63346 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((-F(3)) \times (F(3!) - F(4!))) - (F(6))!) \\63347 &:= ((6! \times ((F(3)^{3!}) + 4!)) - F(7)) \\63348 &:= (((F(6) \times (3!)!) - 3) \times 4) + 8! \\63349 &:= (((F(6) \times (3!)!) - F(F(3))) \times (F(F(4)) + 9)) \\63352 &:= (F(6) \times (((3!)! \times (3! + (5))) - F(2))) \\63353 &:= (((6! - F(3!))^{F(3)} - 5!) / F(3!)) \\63354 &:= (((-6!) \times F(3!)) \times (-3! + (5))) - (F(4))! \\63355 &:= (((-6!) \times F(3!)) \times (-3! + (5))) - (5) \\63357 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((3 \times 3)! / 5!) - (7))) \\63359 &:= (((6! - F(3!)) \times F((3! + (5)))) - 9) \\ \\63360 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 0 \\63361 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 1 \\63362 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 2 \\63363 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 3 \\63364 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 4 \\63365 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 5 \\63366 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 6 \\63367 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 7 \\63368 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 8 \\63369 &:= (F(6) + 3) \times F(3!) \times 6! + 9 \\ \\63371 &:= ((F(6) + 3) \times ((3!)! + (7! + 1))) \\63377 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (3! - ((F(3!) - F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)))) \\63379 &:= ((6 - 3) + ((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) \times F(9))) \\63381 &:= (F(F(6)) - ((3!)! \times (-F((3 + 8)) - 1))) \\63382 &:= ((F(6) + 3) \times (((3!)! \times 8) + 2)) \\63384 &:= ((6! \times F((F(3) \times 3!))) - ((8! - 4!)) \\63386 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (((3! - (3^8)) \times F(6)))) \\63387 &:= ((F(6))! + (((F(3) + 3))! - (F(8))) \times F(F(7))) \\63389 &:= (F(F(6)) + (((3!)! - F(3!)) \times 89)) \\63392 &:= ((F(6))! - ((F(F(3)) + 3!) \times (-F(9) - 2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63393 &:= (((F(6) \times (3!)!) + 3) \times (9 + F(3))) \\ 63394 &:= (((F((F(6) + 3)) \times (3!)!) + F(9)) - ((F(4))!)) \\ 63396 &:= -(((F(6))! + (3! \times (-3!) + (-9!)/F(F(6)))))) \\ 63408 &:= (-6) \times (F((F(3!) + (F(4))!)) + (0! - F(F(8)))) \\ 63414 &:= (6 \times (F((-3) + 4!)) - (F(14))) \\ 63423 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F(3!)) \times (F(4)^{F(2)+3!})) \\ 63425 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))}) \times (-F(2) - 5!))) \\ 63426 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F((F(3!) + (F(4))!))) + 2) \times 6) \\ 63427 &:= (((F((F(F(6)) - 3!)) \times F((F(4))!)) - F(2)) \times F(7)) \\ 63432 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3!) \times (F(4)^{F(3!)})) - 2)) \\ 63433 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(3!) \times (F(4)^{F(3!)})) - F(F(3)))) \\ 63434 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((3^{4+3}) \times 4!)) \\ 63435 &:= (6! + (F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))) \times (3 \times 5))) \\ 63436 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(3) + ((F(4)^{F(3!)} \times F(6)))) \\ 63436 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(3) + ((F(4)^{F(3!)} \times F(6)))) \\ 63437 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (3 - (4! \times (-3^7)))) \\ 63438 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (-4 + F((3! + 8)))) \\ 63440 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) - 3!)) \times F((F(4))!)) \times F(((F(4))! + 0!))) \\ 63442 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(3!) \times ((F(4)^{F(F(4)!)} + F(2)))) \\ 63444 &:= ((F(6))! - (((F(3) + F(4))! - F(4!))/F(F(4)))) \\ 63447 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((3^{F(F(4)!)} \times F((F(4))!)) + F(7))) \\ 63448 &:= ((6! + F(F(3))) \times ((4! \times 4) - 8)) \\ 63449 &:= (((F(6))! - F(F(3!))) + (((F(4!)/F(F(4))) - F(9)))) \\ 63452 &:= (((F(6))! + F(3!)) + ((F(4!) - 5!)/2)) \\ 63454 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + ((F(4!) - ((5^4)))) \\ 63456 &:= (((6! + 3) \times (F(F(4))^5)) + (F(6))!) \\ 63457 &:= (F((F(6) + 3)) \times (((F(4))! \times 5!) - 7)) \\ 63458 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 3!) \times 4!)/5 + F(F(8))) \\ 63464 &:= (((6! - F(3!)) \times 4!) + F(6)) + F(4!) \\ 63468 &:= (6 \times ((F(3!) \times (-46)) + F(F(8)))) \\ 63469 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + ((F(4!) - (F((6 + 9)))))) \\ 63473 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) - ((F(4))! + (F(7)^3))) \\ 63474 &:= (((6! + F(3)) + (4^7)) + F(4!)) \\ 63475 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) + (4! - 7!)) \times 5) \end{aligned}$$

- 63477 := $(-(6) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-(F(4)! + (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7)))))))$
- 63479 := $((((F(6))! \times F(3)) - F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(7))!/(-9!)))$
- 63483 := $((((F(6))! + F(3)) - F(4!)) \times F(8))/(-F(3))$
- 63486 := $((6 \times (((3!)! \times 4!) + (F(8)))) - (F(6))!)$
- 63492 := $((((F(6))!/F(F(3!))) + 4) \times (F(9) - F(2)))$
- 63493 := $(((F(6))! + 3!) - ((F(4!) - F(9))/(-F(3))))$
- 63495 := $((F(F(6)) + 3!!) \times (F(4))!) + (9^5)$
- 63498 := $(-(6) + (F(F(3!)) \times (F((F(4) + 9)) \times F(8))))$
- 63502 := $(((F(6))! - F(3)) - (F(((5 - 0!)!)/(-2)))$
- 63503 := $-(((F(6))! - ((-(3 - 50))^3)))$
- 63504 := $(F(F(6)) \times (3! \times 504))$
- 63512 := $(((F(6))! + F(3!)) - (F(((5 - 1)!)/(-2)))$
- 63516 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) - (F((5 - 1) \times 6!))$
- 63528 := $(6 \times (((-3) \times 5!) + 2) + F(F(8)))$
- 63533 := $((F(F(6)) \times (F((F(3) \times 5))^{F(3)})) + F(3!))$
- 63534 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((3 \times 5!) - 3)) \times (F(4))!)$
- 63536 := $((6! + F(3)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times F(6)))$
- 63536 := $((6! + F(3)) \times ((5 + 3!) \times F(6)))$
- 63537 := $(-(F(F(6))) + (3! \times ((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(F(7))))$
- 63538 := $((((6! - 3!) \times F((5 + 3!))) - 8)$
- 63543 := $(((F(6))! - F(F(3!))) - ((-5!) - F(4!))/F(3))$
- 63544 := $((((F(6))! + (F(3!) \times 5)) + (F(4!)/F(F(4))))$
- 63546 := $((6! - 3!) \times F(((5!/4!) + (6))))$
- 63548 := $((((6! - F(3!)) \times 5!) - (F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))))$
- 63549 := $((F((F(F(6)) - F(3))) + ((5! \times 4!))) \times 9)$
- 63551 := $((F(6) \times (((F(3!))!/5) - 5!)) - 1)$
- 63552 := $(F(6) \times (((F(3!))!/5) - ((5! \times F(2))))$
- 63553 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(3!))! \times 5) + (5)))/(-3))$
- 63554 := $((F(6) \times (((F(3!))!/5) - 5!)) + F(F(4)))$
- 63558 := $(6 - (((F(3!))!/5) - 5!) \times (-8))$
- 63564 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((3 \times 5!) - F(6))) \times (F(4))!)$
- 63565 := $-(((F(6))! - ((F((3! \times 5))/F(6)) - 5!)))$
- 63576 := $((((6 + 3) \times F((5 + F(7)))) + (F(6))!)$
- 63579 := $((((F(6))! + 3) + (F((5 + F(7))) \times 9))$
- 63588 := $(6 \times ((3! \times (-58)) + F(F(8))))$

- 63594 := (((F(F(F(6)))) + ((3!)! - 5!) × 9) - (F((F(4))!))!)
- 63605 := (((F(6))!/3) - ((6! - 0!)) × 5)
- 63617 := (F(6) + (F(F(3!)) × (F((6 + 1)) × F(F(7))))))
- 63624 := ((6! + 3) × ((F(6)²) + 4!))
- 63627 := (-(6!) - ((-3) - 6!) × F((-2) + F(7)))
- 63628 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 3!) + (F(6) × (-2⁸)))
- 63630 := ((6!/F(3!)) × (6! - F((3! + 0!))))
- 63635 := (((6! + 3) - F(6)) × F((3! + 5)))
- 63636 := (((F(F(F(6)))) + ((3!)! - F(6))) × F(3)) + (F(6))!
- 63636 := (((F(F(F(6)))) + ((3!)! - F(6))) × F(3)) + (F(6))!
- 63639 := ((F(6))! + (((3!⁶)/F(3)) - 9))
- 63642 := (((F(6))! - 3!) - ((6^{F(4)})/(-2)))
- 63643 := (((F(6))! × 3) - F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(4!) + 3)))
- 63644 := (F((F(6) × 3)) + ((6! × 4!) - (4)))
- 63645 := ((F(F(6)) × (F((F(3) + F(6)))^{F(F(4))})) + 5!)
- 63646 := (((F(F(6)) × (3!)!)/(-F(6))) + (4^{F(6)}))
- 63647 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (F((3! + F(6)))))) × (F(4))!) + F(F(7)))
- 63648 := (((6! + F(3)) × 6) × 4!) - 8!
- 63651 := ((F(6))! + ((3 × ((6⁵) + 1))))
- 63652 := ((F(6))! + ((-((3!)! - F(F(F(6)))) × (-F((5 - 2))))))
- 63654 := ((F(6))! + (((F(3) + (6⁵)) × F(4))))
- 63655 := ((6 × (F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(6))!/(-5!))) - (5))
- 63656 := ((F(6))! - (-(3 × (6⁵)) - F(6)))
- 63660 := ((F(F(F(6))) × 3!) - (((F(6))!/(F(F(6)) - 0!))))
- 63664 := ((F(6))! + (((3! + F(F(F(6)))) + (6!)) × F(F(4))))
- 63668 := ((F(6))! + (F(3) × ((F(6) + 6!) + F(F(8)))))
- 63672 := (F(F(6)) × (F(3!) + (F(F(6)) × F((F(7) - F(2))))))
- 63678 := ((F(6))! + (F(3) × ((6! + F(7)) + F(F(8)))))
- 63679 := (((-6!) - F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) × (-F(7))) - F(9))
- 63687 := ((F(F(6)) - F(3!)) × (6 - (-F(8)) × F(F(7))))
- 63693 := (F(F(6)) × (F(3!) + ((F(F(6)) + F(9))^{F(3)})))
- 63696 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (3! × (F(F(6)) + F(9)))) × 6)
- 63713 := ((F(F(6)) + F(3!)) × (F(7)^{1×3}))
- 63720 := (-F(6)! + 3! × F(F(7)))/2 + 0

- $63721 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 1$
 $63722 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 2$
 $63723 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 3$
 $63724 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 4$
 $63725 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 5$
 $63726 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 6$
 $63727 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 7$
 $63728 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 8$
 $63729 := (-F(6)! + 3!! \times F(F(7)))/2 + 9$
- $63734 := (((F(F(6)) + F(3!)) \times (F(7)^3)) + F(F((F(4)!)))$
 $63738 := (6 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F(F(7)) + ((3!)/8)))$
 $63742 := ((F(F(6)) + F(3!)) \times ((F(7)^{F(4)} + F(2)))$
 $63743 := (((F(6)! + 3!) + F(F(7))) - (F(4!)/(-F(3))))$
 $63748 := (-F(6) - ((-((F(3) - F(7))) \times F(4!))/(-8)))$
 $63756 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) - (((F(7) - (5)))! / F(F(6))))$
 $63763 := (((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) + 7) - ((F(6)! / F(F(3!))))$
 $63764 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) - ((F(F(7)) + 6) \times F((F(4)!)))$
 $63766 := ((F(6) \times (((3!)! \times F(7)) - F(F(6)))) - F(F(F(6))))$
 $63774 := (6 \times ((-3) + 7!) - (F(F(7)) \times (-4!)))$
 $63778 := ((F(F(6)) - F(3!)) \times (F(7) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(8))))$
 $63782 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(3!) - (7!)) \times F(8)) / (-2)))$
 $63786 := (((F(6)! / (-F(3)^7)) + F(F(8))) \times 6)$
 $63788 := (((((F(6)! \times F(3)) + (7!)) - F(F(8))) - F(F(8)))$
 $63791 := (((6! - 3!) - F(7)) \times 91)$
 $63793 := (-(((F(6)! - F((F(3) \times F(7)))) + (-9!) / F(F(3!))))$
 $63794 := ((F(F(F(6))) + F((-((3 - 7)))!)) + (9 \times ((F(4)!)!))$
 $63795 := -((F((F(F(6)) - F(F(3)))) + (7! \times (-9 + 5))))$
 $63796 := (-6!) + ((F(F(3!)) + F(F(7)))^{F(9-6)})$
 $63798 := (((F(F(6)) - F(3!)) \times F(F(7))) + 9) \times F(8)$
 $63804 := (6 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F((8 - 0!) \times 4!)))$
 $63813 := ((6! - 3) \times F(((8 \times 1) + 3)))$
 $63824 := (((F(F(6)))! / ((-3) + F(8)))! - 2) \times F((F(4)!))$
 $63832 := (F(6) \times (((F(F(3!)))! / ((F(8) - 3)!)) - F(2)))$
 $63834 := (-6) + ((F(3!) \times (F(8)!)) / ((3! \times F(4)!))$

$$63835 := (((F(F(6)))!)/(((-(3) + F(8))!)/F(3!))) - (5))$$

$$63837 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((-(3!) + F(F((F(8)/3)))) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$63840 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 0$$

$$63841 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 1$$

$$63842 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 2$$

$$63843 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 3$$

$$63844 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 4$$

$$63845 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 5$$

$$63846 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 6$$

$$63847 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 7$$

$$63848 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 8$$

$$63849 := F(6)! \times 38/4! + 9$$

$$63855 := ((6! - (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(8)))) \times 55)$$

$$63856 := (-(6!) + (F(3!) \times ((8!/5) + F(6))))$$

$$63858 := (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(3!) - ((F(8) \times 5!) \times F(8))))$$

$$63864 := (((6! + 3!) \times F(8)) + 6!) \times 4)$$

$$63865 := (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(F(3)) - ((-F(8)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-5!))))$$

$$63866 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((3!)! \times (-F(8))) \times F(F(6)))/(-6))$$

$$63872 := (F(F(F(6))) + (3! - ((F(8) \times 7!)/(-2))))$$

$$63874 := (F(F(F(6))) + (F(3!) + ((F(8) \times 7!)/F(F(4))))$$

$$63876 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3!) - ((8 - F(F(7))) \times (-F(6))))$$

$$63888 := (((6! - F(3)) + 8) \times 88)$$

$$63894 := (((6! - F(3)) \times 89) - F((F(4))!))$$

$$63896 := (((6! - F(3)) \times 89) - (6))$$

$$63902 := ((6! - F(3)) \times F((9 + 02)))$$

$$63923 := (F(F(6)) - (F((F(3) + 9)) \times (2 - 3!)))$$

$$63933 := ((6^{3!}) + ((9!/F(F(3!))) - 3))$$

$$63934 := ((6^{3!}) + ((9!/F(F(3!))) - F(F(4))))$$

$$63937 := (((F(6))! + F((3! + (F(9)/F(3)))) - (7!))$$

$$63942 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (-((F(3) - 9))!)) \times 4) - 2)$$

$$63943 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (-((F(3) - 9))!)) \times 4) - F(F(3)))$$

$$63944 := ((((-6) - F(3)) + F(9))^{F(4)} + F(4!))$$

$$63947 := ((6 + ((F(3!) + 9)^{F(4)})) \times F(7))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63948 &:= (6 \times ((-(3+9)) \times 4!) + F(F(8))) \\ 63953 &:= (F(6) + ((F(F(3!)) + ((9!/5!))) \times F(F(3!))) \\ 63954 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (F(3)^9)) \times 5!) - (F(4)!)) \\ 63955 &:= ((6! \times F((F(3) + 9))) + (-5 - 5!)) \\ 63960 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (F(3)^9)) \times ((6 - 0!))!) \\ 63964 &:= ((-6) \times 3!) + ((F(9) + (6))^{F(4)}) \\ 63966 &:= ((F((F(F(6)) - F(3))) - (-9 \times 6!)) \times 6) \\ 63974 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F(3!)) \times (9 + (F(7)^{F(4)}))) \\ 63976 &:= ((F(6) \times (F(3) + 9)) \times (7 + 6!)) \\ 63979 &:= -((F(F(6)) - ((3! + F(9))^{F(F(7)-9)})) \\ 63984 &:= (((6! \times ((3!)! - 9))/8) - (F(4)!)) \\ 63985 &:= (((F((F(6) + 3!)) \times (-F(9))) + (F(8))) \times (-5)) \\ 63986 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (((3!)! - ((9! - 8!)/6))) \\ 63987 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((3!)! \times (-F(9)))/(-8) - F(7))) \\ 63991 &:= ((6! - F(F(3))) \times (F(9) + F((9 + 1)))) \\ 63993 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 39) - 9!) - F(F(3!))) \\ 63999 &:= ((6! \times F((F(3) + 9))) - (9 \times 9)) \\ 64003 &:= ((F((6!/4!)) - 0!)/F((0! + 3!))) \\ 64008 &:= ((F(6))! - (-4! \times F(((0! + 0!) \times 8))) \\ 64024 &:= (-((F(F(F(6))) - F((4! + 0!))) - F((2 + F((F(4))!)))) \\ 64032 &:= ((F(6))! - (-4! \times (0! + F((F(3!) \times 2)))) \\ 64033 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(4!) - 0!)) + ((F(3!)!)/3!)) \\ 64034 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F(4!)) + ((0 - (F(3!)!)/(-F(4)!))) \\ 64037 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((4! + 0!)) - (3! \times 7)))) \\ 64038 &:= (-6) \times ((F((F(4))! + 0!)) \times F(F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \\ 64039 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((4! + 0!)) - (3! + F(9)))))) \\ 64043 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 0!)) - ((F(4))!^{F(3)}))) \\ 64044 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((F(4))!) \times F((0! + F((F(4))!)))) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 64045 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 0!)) - F((4 + 5)))) \\ 64048 &:= ((-6) - ((F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!)^{F(4)})) \times (-8) \\ 64049 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 0!)) - (-4 + F(9)))) \\ 64053 &:= -(((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((4! + 0!)) - 5))) + F(F(3!))) \\ 64054 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (((4 + 0!)^5) \times 4!)) \\ 64055 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (4!)) \times (-0!)) + F((5 \times 5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64057 &:= (((F(6))! + F((4! - 0!))) + (5! - 7!)) \\
 64058 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - F(4!)) - F((((0 \times 5))! + F(8)))) \\
 64059 &:= (- (F(F(6))) - (-(((F(4))!)! \times F((F(F(-(0! - (5)))))) + 9)))) \\
 64063 &:= (((- (F(6)) + F(4!)) + F((0! + F(F(6)))) - F(3!)) \\
 64064 &:= ((F(6) + ((F(4))!)!) \times (- (0!) + F((F(6) + F(4)))) \\
 64065 &:= (((((F(6))! - F(4!)) - F((- (0!) + F(F(6)))))) \times (-5)) \\
 64066 &:= ((- ((F(F(6)) - F(4!))) + F((0! + F(F(6)))) + F(6)) \\
 64067 &:= ((6! \times F((F(4) + F(06)))) - F(7)) \\
 64069 &:= (((F((F(F(6)) + 4)) - 0!) - F(F(F(6)))) - 9) \\
 64071 &:= ((- (F(6)) + F(4!)) + F((0! + F((7 + 1)))) \\
 64072 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((4! + 0!)) - 7))) \times (-F(2)) \\
 64073 &:= ((- (6) + F(4!)) + F((0! + ((7 \times 3)))) \\
 64074 &:= ((6! \times F((4 + 07))) - (F(4))!) \\
 64075 &:= ((6! \times F((4 + 07))) - (5)) \\
 64077 &:= -(((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) - F(-(((0! - F(7)) - F(7)))))) \\
 64078 &:= (((- (F(6)) + F((4! + 0!))) + 7) - F(F(8))) \\
 \\
 64080 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 0 \\
 64081 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 1 \\
 64082 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 2 \\
 64083 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 3 \\
 64084 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 4 \\
 64085 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 5 \\
 64086 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 6 \\
 64087 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 7 \\
 64088 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 8 \\
 64089 &:= 6! \times F(F(4) + 08) + 9 \\
 \\
 64092 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 0!)) + F((9 - 2)))) \\
 64094 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((4! + 0!)) + (- (9) + 4!)))) \\
 64095 &:= ((6 + (((F(4))! + 0!))!) + (9^5)) \\
 64097 &:= (F(6) + ((F(4))^{0!+9} + 7!)) \\
 64099 &:= ((- (F(F(F(6)))) + F(F((F(4))!))) + (- (0!) + F((F(9) - 9)))) \\
 64101 &:= (F(F(6)) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-F((10 + 1)))) \\
 64103 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 1)) + ((0! + 3)!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 64104 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 1)) + (0! + 4!))))$
- 64108 := $((F(((6!/4!) + 1)) - 0!)/F(8))$
- 64113 := $-(((F(F(F(6))) - F((4! + 1))) - F((1 + F(3!))))))$
- 64114 := $(F((6 + F(4))) + (F(11) \times ((F(4))!))$
- 64116 := $((6^{F(F(4))}) + ((F(11) \times 6!))$
- 64134 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (4! + F(13))) \times (F(4))!)$
- 64143 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 1)) + (4^3))))$
- 64146 := $(6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-1 + (F(F(4))^{F(6)}))))$
- 64146 := $(6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-1 + (F(F(4))^{F(6)}))))$
- 64148 := $(- (F(F(6))) - (((F(4))!)! + 1) \times (-F((F(4) + 8))))$
- 64163 := $((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (1 + 6!)) - 3!)$
- 64169 := $((6! + F(F(F(4)))) \times F((-1 + F(F(6))) - 9))$
- 64199 := $-((F(F(F(6))) + (-((4 + 1)!) - F((F(9) - 9))))$
- 64223 := $((F(6))! + (((F(4!) - 2)/2) + 3!!))$
- 64224 := $((F(6) \times (4!^{F(2+2)})) - F(4!))$
- 64226 := $((F(6))! - ((F(4!)/(-2)) + (-2 - 6!))$
- 64232 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) + ((-2 - 3!!) \times 2))$
- 64233 := $((F(6))! + ((F(4!)/2) + ((3^3!))))$
- 64234 := $((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (2 + 3!!)) - (4!))$
- 64236 := $((6 \times F(F((4 \times 2)))) - ((F(3) \times 6!))$
- 64237 := $((F(6))! + (((F(4!)/2) + 3!!) + F(7)))$
- 64238 := $(((-6!) \times F(F(4))) + 2) + (3! \times F(F(8)))$
- 64239 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((F((F((F(4))!) + 2))^{F(3)} + F(9)))$
- 64242 := $((6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) + F(2))) + (((F(4))!)! \times (-2)))$
- 64244 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((2 \times ((F(4))!)! - F((F(4))!)))$
- 64247 := $-((F(F(F(6))) - ((F((4! + F(2))) + (4! \times 7))))$
- 64248 := $(6! + ((F(4!)/2) + (4! + 8!))$
- 64249 := $((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (2 + ((F(4))!)!)) - 9)$
- 64254 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(4) + (-2 \times 5!))) \times (F(4))!)$
- 64256 := $((F(F(6)) \times 4!) - 2) \times (5! + F(6))$
- 64257 := $(- (F(F(6))) + ((F(4))! \times (F(F(F((F(2) + 5)))) - F(F(7))))$
- 64258 := $((6! + F(F(4))) \times F(-(((2 - 5) - 8)))$
- 64264 := $((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (2 + 6!)) + (F(4))!)$
- 64266 := $((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (2 + 6!)) + F(6))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64269 &:= (((-F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(((F(4))! + F(2)))))) \times (-6)) - 9) \\
 64271 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(2) + F(F(7)))))) - 1) \\
 64273 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(2) + F(F(7)))))) + F(F(3))) \\
 64276 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F((4! - (2 - 7)))) / (-F(6))) \\
 64277 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-F(2) + F(F(7)))))) - 7) \\
 64284 &:= (((6! - 4!) \times (-2)) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(4))!)) \\
 64286 &:= (F(6) + ((F(F(((F(4))! + F(2)))) - F(F(8))) \times (-6))) \\
 64287 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(4))! \times ((-2) + F(F(8))) - F(F(7)))) \\
 64296 &:= ((6^{F(4)}) + (F((2 + 9)) \times 6!)) \\
 64307 &:= (((-6) \times F((4! + F(F(3)))))) + 0!) / (-7) \\
 64313 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (3!!) + (F(13))) \\
 64314 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (F(4))!) - F(F((3! + 1)))) \times (F(4))!) \\
 64315 &:= ((6! + (((4!!) / (F(F(3!!)))! - 1)) \times 5) \\
 64324 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (F(4))!) + F(3!))^2 + F(4!)) \\
 64325 &:= (((((F(6))! / F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(2)) \times 5) \\
 64326 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(4))!)) - F(F((3! + F(2)))))) \times 6) \\
 64330 &:= (((F(6))! / F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (3! - 0!) \\
 64332 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-F(3!)^2))) \\
 64335 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(4)))) + ((F(3!!) / F(F(3!)))) \times 5) \\
 64336 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (3!!) + (F(3)^{F(6)})) \\
 64337 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(4))) + F(3)) \times ((3!!) - F(7))) \\
 64339 &:= (-F(6) + ((F(4) + 3!!) \times F((F(3) + 9)))) \\
 64344 &:= (((F(F(6)) + 4) \times (3!!) + F(4!)) - (4!)) \\
 64345 &:= (F((F(F(6)) + 4) - (F((F(3!) + F(4))) \times 5!)) \\
 64346 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - F((4! - F(3)))) - ((F(4))!^6)) \\
 64346 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - F((4! - F(3)))) - ((F(4))!^6)) \\
 64347 &:= (((6! - F(4)) + 3!) \times F((4 + 7))) \\
 \\
 64350 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 0 \\
 64351 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 1 \\
 64352 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 2 \\
 64353 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 3 \\
 64354 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 4 \\
 64355 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 5 \\
 64356 &:= 6! / F(F(4))! \times (3!! - 5) + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$64357 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (3!! - 5) + 7$$

$$64358 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (3!! - 5) + 8$$

$$64359 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (3!! - 5) + 9$$

$$64360 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(4!)/3!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!))$$

$$64361 := (((6^{F(4)!}) - 3!) + F((F(F(6)) + 1)))$$

$$64362 := ((-6!) + (F(4) \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))))) \times 2$$

$$64363 := (-((F(F(6)) - (F(4!)/(-F(3)))))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(3!))$$

$$64364 := (((6^{F(4)!}) + F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))))) - F(4)$$

$$64365 := ((F((F(F(6)) - (F(4)!)) + 3) \times (F(F(6)) \times 5))$$

$$64366 := (((F(F(6)) - ((F(4)!))!) - F((F(3!) + F(F(6)))))) / (-F(6))$$

$$64367 := ((6^{F(4)!}) + F(((3 + 6) + F(7))))$$

$$64368 := ((6! + F(4!)) - ((-3) \times 6!) \times 8)$$

$$64372 := (((F(6)!/4) + 3) + (F(F(7))^2))$$

$$64374 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 74))$$

$$64377 := (((F(6)!/4) + F(3!)) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(7))))$$

$$64379 := (((F(6)! + F(F((F(4)!)))) - (((3!)! - F(7)) \times (-F(9))))$$

$$64380 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 0$$

$$64381 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 1$$

$$64382 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 2$$

$$64383 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 3$$

$$64384 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 4$$

$$64385 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 5$$

$$64386 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 6$$

$$64387 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 7$$

$$64388 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 8$$

$$64389 := -6^4 + 3! \times F(F(8)) + 9$$

$$64394 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 3!) - ((F(9)^{F(F(4))})))$$

$$64398 := (((F(6) + (F(4!)/F(F(3!)))) \times F(9)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$64404 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(F(((F(4)! + 0!)))) \times (F(4)!))$$

$$64416 := ((-6!) + (-F(4!)/F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (-1 - F(F(6))))$$

$$64423 := -((F((F(6) + (F(4)!))!) - (((F(4)!)^2)/F(3!))))$$

$$64428 := (6 \times ((F((F(4)!)) \times (-4! + 2)) + F(F(8))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64433 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (4 + 3!!)) - 3) \\
 64434 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (4 + 3!!)) - F(F(4))) \\
 64435 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(F(4)))^{F(4)} + 3!!) \times 5) \\
 64436 &:= (F((F(6) + F(4))) \times ((4!/3!) + 6!)) \\
 \\
 64440 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 0 \\
 64441 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 1 \\
 64442 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 2 \\
 64443 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 3 \\
 64444 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 4 \\
 64445 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 5 \\
 64446 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 6 \\
 64447 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 7 \\
 64448 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 8 \\
 64449 &:= (6! - 4) \times F(4)!!/F(F(4)!) + 9 \\
 \\
 64454 &:= (6 + (F((F(4)!) \times (((F((F(4)!)!)/5) - F((F(4)!)!)))) \\
 64456 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4)!) - (F(F(4)) \times F((5!/F(6)))) \\
 64457 &:= ((F(6) \times (-((F(4)!) + ((F((F(4)!)!)/5))) - 7) \\
 64458 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4)!) - (F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times 58)) \\
 64464 &:= ((6! + F(4!)) + ((4 + 6!) \times 4!)) \\
 64466 &:= (((((F(6))! - ((F(4)!)!)/F(4) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6))!) \\
 64467 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((4^{F(4)!}) + F(F(6))) \times F(7))) \\
 64473 &:= (-6!) + ((4^{F(F(4)!)} - (7^3))) \\
 64474 &:= (-((F(F(6)) \times F(F(4)))) + ((F(F((F(4)!)!)) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4)!)}) \\
 64475 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (F(4)!) \times (F(4)!) - (F(F(7)) \times 5)) \\
 64476 &:= (6! + ((F(4!) \times (4 + 7))/F(6))) \\
 64477 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(4) - (4 \times 7!))) \times (-7)) \\
 64478 &:= (((-(((6 \times 4)!)/F(F((F(4)!)!)))! - (-7) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 64485 &:= (F(F(6)) + (F((F(4)!) \times (-((F(4)!)! - (8!/5)))) \\
 64488 &:= (-6) \times (((F(4)!) + (4! \times 8)) - F(F(8))) \\
 64491 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((F(4)!) \times (F(F(4))^9) - 1)) \\
 64492 &:= (((-F(F(6))) + ((F(4)!)! + F(F(4))) \times 92) \\
 64494 &:= ((F(6))! + (F((F(4) \times F(4))) \times (-9) + ((F(4)!)!)) \\
 64495 &:= (-((F(F(6)) - 4) + (((F((F(4)!)!))! - 9!)/(-5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 64496 := (((F(6) × F(4!)) - F(F(4))) - 9!) × F(6))
- 64498 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((4^{F(F(4)!)}) + 9!)/8))
- 64499 := (((F(F(F(6))) × (F(4)!) - F(F((F(4)!))) - (F(9) × F(9))))
- 64502 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) - 0!)) - 2)
- 64503 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) - (0! + F(3!)))
- 64504 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) - F((F(04)!))!))
- 64506 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) - 06)
- 64507 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) + 0!)) - F(7))
- 64508 := (((F(F(F(6))) + (((F(4)!!) × (-5!)) × (-0!)) - F(F(8)))
- 64510 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) - (1 + 0!))
- 64511 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) - (1 × 1))
- 64512 := ((F(6)^{F(4)}) × (5! + ((1 + 2)!))
- 64513 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + (1³))
- 64514 := (((((F(6)!) × (-4))/(-5)) + 1) × F(F(4)))
- 64515 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + F(-((1 - 5))))
- 64517 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) - 1)) + F(7))
- 64518 := (6 - (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) × (-1 × 8)))
- 64520 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + F(((2 + 0)!))!))
- 64521 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) + F(2))) + 1)
- 64522 := (6 + ((F(F((F(4)!)) + (F(F((5 + 2))))))²))
- 64523 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) + F(2))) + 3)
- 64524 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + (2 × (F(4)!))
- 64525 := (F((F(6) + F(4))) × (5 + ((F(2) + (5)!))!))
- 64526 := (6 - (((F((F(4)!))!)/(-5)) - F(2)) × F(6)))
- 64527 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + (2 + F(7)))
- 64528 := (((((F(6)!) × 4!)/(-5!)) - 2) × (-8))
- 64529 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) + F(2))) + 9)
- 64530 := ((6! - F(4)) × (5! - (30)))
- 64532 := ((((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + F(F(3!))) - F(2))
- 64533 := (((6! - F(4)) × F((5 + 3!))) + 3!))
- 64534 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) - ((F(3) - 4!)))
- 64536 := (((((F(6)!) × 4!)/5!) + 3) × F(6))
- 64539 := (((-((F(6)!) × F((F(4)!)))/(-5)) + (3 × 9))
- 64542 := ((F(6) × (((F((F(4)!))!)/5) + 4)) - 2)

$$\begin{aligned}
 64543 &:= ((F(6) \times (((F((F(4)))!)/5) + 4)) - F(F(3))) \\
 64544 &:= ((6! - ((F(4!) - 5!)/(-F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 64546 &:= (((-((F(6))!) \times F((F(4))!))/(-5)) + F((F(4) + (6)))) \\
 64546 &:= (((-((F(6))!) \times F((F(4))!))/(-5)) + F((F(4) + (6)))) \\
 64547 &:= (((F(F(6))^{F(4)}) - (5!/F(4))) \times 7) \\
 64548 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((5! + F(F((F(4))!))) \times 8)) \\
 64549 &:= (((-((F(6))!) \times F((F(4))!))/(-5)) + (F(4) + F(9))) \\
 64551 &:= ((F(6) \times (((F((F(4)))!)/5) + (5))) - 1) \\
 64552 &:= (F(6) \times (((F((F(4))!)/5) + (5 \times F(2)))) \\
 64553 &:= ((F(6) \times (((F((F(4))!)/5) + (5))) + F(F(3))) \\
 64554 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F((F(4) \times 5)) \times 5) + (4!))) \\
 64558 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) + (4! \times (-((5⁵)) - F(8)))))) \\
 \\
 64560 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 0 \\
 64561 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 1 \\
 64562 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 2 \\
 64563 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 3 \\
 64564 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 4 \\
 64565 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 5 \\
 64566 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 6 \\
 64567 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 7 \\
 64568 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 8 \\
 64569 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(4))!)/5 + 6 + 9 \\
 \\
 64574 &:= (6 + (((F((F(4))!)/(-5)) - 7) \times (-F((F(4))!)))) \\
 64575 &:= (((F(F(6)) + ((F(4))!) + 5!) \times 75) \\
 64576 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-4)) + ((5! + 7!) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 64578 &:= (((F(6))! + ((4⁵) \times F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\
 64584 &:= ((F(6))! + ((4! + F((-5) + F(8)))) \times 4!) \\
 64586 &:= (((((F(6))!/F(4)) - 5!) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!) \\
 64592 &:= (F(6) \times (((F((F(4))!)/5) + (9 + F(2)))) \\
 64593 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((5! \times 9) + 3)) \\
 64594 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((5! \times 9) + F(F(4)))) \\
 64596 &:= (((6! \times F(4)) \times 5) - F(9)) \times 6) \\
 64597 &:= (((F(-((F(6) - 4!))) \times 5) + F(9)) \times F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$64614 := ((6! + (F(4))!) \times F(((6 + 1) + 4)))$$

$$64620 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 0$$

$$64621 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 1$$

$$64622 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 2$$

$$64623 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 3$$

$$64624 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 4$$

$$64625 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 5$$

$$64626 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 6$$

$$64627 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 7$$

$$64628 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 8$$

$$64629 := 6!/F(F(4)!) \times (6! - 2) + 9$$

$$64632 := (-F(6) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - (((6!/F(3!))^2))))$$

$$64635 := (F(F(6)) + (((F(4))! + (6!)) \times F((3! + (5)))))$$

$$64638 := (((F(6))^{F(4)} \times 6) + 3!) \times F(8)$$

$$64644 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(4))!)) - (6!/4)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$64647 := ((6!/(-4)) + ((F(F(6))^{F(4)} \times 7))$$

$$64648 := -((F(6) - (((4! - (6))^4) - 8!))$$

$$64652 := -((F(F(F(6))) + (((F(4))!)! \times (F(F(6)) \times (-5))) + 2))$$

$$64653 := ((((-((F(6))!) \times F((F(4))!)) - (6!)) / (-5)) - 3)$$

$$64655 := (((F(6))! \times F((F(4))!)) + (6! - (5))) / 5$$

$$64656 := ((-6) + 4!) \times ((6! \times 5) - F(6))$$

$$64658 := ((-6!) + F(4!)) - (((F(6))! / (-5)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$64662 := (6 \times (((F((F(4))!) \times (-F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(2)))$$

$$64664 := ((F(6))! + (F((F(4) + (6))) \times (6! - (4))))$$

$$64668 := (6 \times (-((4! + F((6 + 6)))) + F(F(8))))$$

$$64672 := (-((6! - (4^{F(6)}))) - F((F(7) - F(2))))$$

$$64674 := (((F(F(6))^{F(4)} - F(F(6))) \times 7) - (F(4))!)$$

$$64675 := ((F(6) + F((4! - F(6)))) \times (F(7) \times 5))$$

$$64677 := (6! + ((4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (7!))) + F(7)))$$

$$64678 := (((((F(6))! + (4!)) + (F(6))!) - (7!)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$64680 := (((F(F(6))^{F(4)} - F(F(6))) \times (8 - 0!))$$

$$64683 := ((-6) - F((4! - F(6)))) + (F(F(8)) \times 3!)$$

$$64686 := ((((-6) \times 4!) - F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times 6$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64687 &:= ((-6) \times (((F(4))! \times F(F(6))) - F(F(8)))) - F(F(7))) \\ 64694 &:= ((F(6))! - (((F(4) - 6!) \times F(9)) + (4))) \\ 64695 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (F(F(4)) \times (6! \times (-9)))) \times (-5)) \\ 64696 &:= ((F(6)^4) - ((6! + 9!)/(-6))) \\ 64697 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) + ((F(6) - F((9 + 7)))))) \\ 64698 &:= (((6! + F(4)) - (6)) \times F(9)) + 8! \\ 64703 &:= (F((F(6) + F(4))) \times (7 + ((03)!))!) \\ 64706 &:= (((F(6))!/F(4)) + F(F((7 + 0!)))) + (F(6))! \\ 64710 &:= ((6!/F((F(4))!)) \times (((7 - 1)! - 0!)) \\ 64711 &:= (F(6) - (((F(4))!)! + 7) \times (-F(11))) \\ 64723 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (F(F(7)) + (((2 \times 3)!))) \\ 64724 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (F(F(7)) - F(2))) - ((F(4))!))! \\ 64727 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times (-F(4))) + (7! + 2)) \times F(7)) \\ 64728 &:= ((6! - 4!) \times (72 + F(8))) \\ 64732 &:= ((F(6))! + (F((-4) + F(7))) \times ((3)! - 2)) \\ 64734 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (4! + F(7))) \times 3!) - ((F(4))!)! \\ 64735 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F((F(4))!))) - (7!)) \times (3! + (5))) \\ 64737 &:= -(((6! + 4!) - ((7! - 3) \times F(7))) \\ 64742 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((F(F(7)) \times 4) + 2)) \\ 64743 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((F(F(7)) \times 4) + F(F(3)))) \\ 64744 &:= ((F((-6) + 4!)) \times 7) + ((F(4))!^{F(4)!}) \\ 64745 &:= ((F(6))! + (((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(F(7))) - F((F(4))!)) \times 5)) \\ 64746 &:= (((-6!) - F(4!)) \times (7 + 4))/(-F(6)) \\ 64746 &:= (((-6!) - F(4!)) \times (7 + 4))/(-F(6)) \\ 64747 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(F(4)))) - (F(7) \times (4 - 7!)) \\ 64748 &:= (-6!) + ((4 - 7!) \times (F((F(4))!) - (F(8)))) \\ 64755 &:= (((F(-((F(6) - 4!))) \times F(7)) + 5!) \times 5) \\ 64757 &:= (((6! - F((F(4))!)) \times F(7)) - (5)) \times 7 \\ 64758 &:= (6 \times ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-F(7))) - (-5!) - F(F(8)))) \\ 64761 &:= -((6! + ((F(4) - 7!) \times F((6 + 1)))) \\ 64764 &:= (6 \times (((F(F(4)) + F(7)) \times 6!) - (F(4))!)) \\ 64765 &:= (((((F(6))!/(-F(4))) - F(F(7))) + (6!)) \times (-5)) \\ 64766 &:= (((6! - F(F(F(4)))) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) + (F(6))! \\ 64767 &:= ((F(6))! - (F((4 \times 7)))/(-6 + 7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64768 &:= (-6!) + (((F(F(4))^{F(7)} - 6) \times 8)) \\
 64769 &:= ((F(6))! - ((4! + (7)) - (6! \times F(9)))) \\
 64770 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (((F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \times F(F(7))) - 0!)) \\
 64772 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(4))) + ((F(7) \times (7! - 2))) \\
 64773 &:= -(((6! + 4!) - ((7! \times F(7)) - 3)) \\
 64774 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(4))) + ((7! \times F(7)) - 4!) \\
 64778 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(F(4)))) + (((7! \times F(7)) - F(8))) \\
 64779 &:= (-6!) - (((F(F(F(4))) + 7!) \times (-F(7))) + F(9)) \\
 64782 &:= (((F(6))! + F(4!)) + ((7 + F(F(8))) \times (-2))) \\
 64783 &:= (((F(6))! + F(4!)) - F(7)) + (F(F(8)) \times (-F(3))) \\
 64785 &:= (((6 + F(F(4))))! - (F(F(7)) \times (F(8) \times (-5)))) \\
 64786 &:= (-6) - (F((4 + 7)) \times (-8 - 6!)) \\
 64787 &:= (((6 + 4)! / (7 \times 8)) - F(7)) \\
 64788 &:= (-6!) + ((F(4))! \times ((-7) + F(F(8))) - (F(8))) \\
 64793 &:= ((6! \times (F(4))!) - (7 - (9! / 3!))) \\
 64794 &:= ((-6!) - (F(4))!) - (7! \times (-9 + 4)) \\
 64795 &:= (((6! \times F(4)) + 7!) \times 9) - (5) \\
 64797 &:= ((F(6))! - ((F(4) + ((7! \times F(9)) / (-7)))) \\
 64798 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(4))) + ((7! \times (F(9) - F(8)))) \\
 64799 &:= ((6! - F((F(4) \times 7))) + F((F(9) - 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64800 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 00 \\
 64801 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 01 \\
 64802 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 02 \\
 64803 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 03 \\
 64804 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 04 \\
 64805 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 05 \\
 64806 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 06 \\
 64807 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 07 \\
 64808 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 08 \\
 64809 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 09 \\
 64810 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 10 \\
 64811 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 11 \\
 64812 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 12 \\
 64813 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 13
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64814 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 14 \\ 64815 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 15 \\ 64816 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 16 \\ 64817 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 17 \\ 64818 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 18 \\ 64819 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 19 \\ 64820 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 20 \\ 64821 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 21 \\ 64822 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 22 \\ 64823 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 23 \\ 64824 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 24 \\ 64825 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 25 \\ 64826 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 26 \\ 64827 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 27 \\ 64828 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 28 \\ 64829 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 29 \\ 64830 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 30 \\ 64831 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 31 \\ 64832 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 32 \\ 64833 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 33 \\ 64834 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 34 \\ 64835 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 35 \\ 64836 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 36 \\ 64837 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 37 \\ 64838 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 38 \\ 64839 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 39 \\ 64840 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 00 \\ 64841 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 41 \\ 64842 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 42 \\ 64843 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 43 \\ 64844 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 44 \\ 64845 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 45 \\ 64846 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 46 \\ 64847 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 47 \\ 64848 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 48 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64849 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 49 \\ 64850 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 50 \\ 64851 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 51 \\ 64852 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 52 \\ 64853 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 53 \\ 64854 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 54 \\ 64855 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 55 \\ 64856 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 56 \\ 64857 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 57 \\ 64858 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 58 \\ 64859 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 59 \\ 64860 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 60 \\ 64861 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 61 \\ 64862 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 62 \\ 64863 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 63 \\ 64864 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 64 \\ 64865 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 65 \\ 64866 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 66 \\ 64867 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 67 \\ 64868 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 68 \\ 64869 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 69 \\ 64870 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 70 \\ 64871 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 71 \\ 64872 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 72 \\ 64873 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 73 \\ 64874 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 74 \\ 64875 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 75 \\ 64876 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 76 \\ 64877 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 77 \\ 64878 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 78 \\ 64879 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 79 \\ 64880 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 80 \\ 64881 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 81 \\ 64882 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 82 \\ 64883 &:= 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 83 \end{aligned}$$

$$64884 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 84$$

$$64885 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 85$$

$$64886 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 86$$

$$64887 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 87$$

$$64888 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 88$$

$$64889 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 89$$

$$64890 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 90$$

$$64891 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 91$$

$$64892 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 92$$

$$64893 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 93$$

$$64894 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 94$$

$$64895 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 95$$

$$64896 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 96$$

$$64897 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 97$$

$$64898 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 98$$

$$64899 := 6!^{F(F(4))} / 8 + 99$$

$$64902 := (((6! + F(4)) \times F(9)) + (F((0! + 2)))!)$$

$$64903 := (((6! + F(4)) \times F(9)) + 0!) + (F(3))!$$

$$64908 := (-(6!) + ((F(4))! \times ((-9) + 0!) + F(F(8))))$$

$$64922 := (((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - F(9)) - ((F((2 + 2)))!))$$

$$64923 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((F(9) - F(2)) + 3!))$$

$$64924 := (((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (F(9) - 2)) - ((F(4))!))$$

$$64928 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (F(9) \times (F(2) + F(8))))$$

$$64931 := -(((F(6))! + ((-4) \times 9!) + F(31)))$$

$$64933 := (((6! + 4) \times F(9)) - 3) + (F(3))!$$

$$64934 := (((F(6))! - F(F(4))) + (F(9) \times ((3!)! + 4)))$$

$$64935 := (((-6!) \times (F(4))!) - 9) \times (-(3 \times 5))$$

$$64936 := (((6! + 4) \times F(9)) + ((F(3) + 6))!)$$

$$64937 := (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (F((9 \times F(3))) - F(7))))$$

$$64938 := (((6! + 4) \times F(9)) + F(3)) + 8!$$

$$64943 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((9 + 4) + 3!))$$

$$64944 := (((6! \times (4! - 9)) + 4!) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$64945 := (((F(6))! / (-4)) + (F(((9 - 4) \times 5))))$$

$$64946 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(4))! - (9^{F(F(4))})) \times (-6!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64946 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(4))! - (9^{F(F(4))})) \times (-6!))) \\ 64947 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (9^{-4+7})) \\ 64948 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times ((F(4))! - F(9))) + (4^8)) \\ 64950 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(-(F(4) - 9)))))) - ((5! + 0!))) \\ 64953 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((4! \times (9 + 5!)) - 3)) \\ 64954 &:= (((F(6))! / (-4)) + 9) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) \\ 64956 &:= ((F((F(6) + (4 + 9))) - 5!) \times 6) \\ 64957 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(4)) + ((9^5) - 7!))) \\ 64958 &:= ((-6!) + F(F(4))) + ((F((9 - 5)))! \times F(F(8))) \\ 64961 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((F(9) \times F(F(6))) + 1)) \\ 64962 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (F(9) \times F((6 + 2)))) \\ 64963 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((-9) + 6!) + F(3)) \\ 64964 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - ((F(9) \times F(F(6))) - F(F(4)))) \\ 64965 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (-9) - (-6 \times 5!)) \\ 64966 &:= (-(((6! + 4!) - F(9))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 6)) \\ 64968 &:= (-(((6! - F(4)) - 9)) + (6 \times F(F(8)))) \\ 64972 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (9 \times F(7)))) - 2) \\ 64973 &:= (F((F(F(6)) - 4)) + ((F(9) \times F(F(7))) \times F(3!))) \\ 64977 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (F((-9) + F(7)) \times F(F(7)))) \\ 64983 &:= (-((6! - (F(4) \times 9))) + (F(F(8)) \times 3!)) \\ 64984 &:= (((6! - 4) \times (F(9) - 8)) + F(4!)) \\ 64987 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(F(4)) + 9) \times (F(F(8)) - (7!)))) \\ 64989 &:= (((6! \times (4! - F(9))) - F(8)) \times (-9)) \\ 64995 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F((4! - 9)) + 9) \times 5)) \\ 64996 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!) - (-F(9) + (F(9) \times F(F(6))))) \\ 65034 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5! - F((0! + 3!)))) \times (F(4))!) \\ 65046 &:= (6 \times ((-5) \times F(F((F(04))!))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65066 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (F((5!/06)) \times (-F(6)))) \\ 65072 &:= ((-(((F(6)^5) + 0!)) + F(F(7))) \times (-2)) \\ 65076 &:= (-((6! - 5!)) + (-((0! - 7)) \times F(F(F(6))))) \\ 65088 &:= (6 \times ((-((5! - 0!)) + F(F(8))) + (F(8)))) \\ 65136 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (((5 + 1))! / F(3!))) \times 6) \\ 65137 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 51) \times 3!) - F(F(7))) \\ 65186 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5!) + (F((-1 + F(8))) \times (-F(6)))) \\ 65196 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (((5 + 1))! / 9)) \times 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65224 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - 5!)^2) - (F((F(2) + 4!)))) \\
 65226 &:= ((-6) \times (5! - F(22))) - (F(6))! \\
 65228 &:= ((6! \times (5! + F(2))) + (-2) \times F(F(8))) \\
 65236 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(F(5 + 2))))^{F(3)} + (6!)) \\
 65237 &:= (F((6 + 5)) \times ((2 \times 3)! + F(7))) \\
 65243 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(5 + 2)))^{F(F(4))}) + F(3!)) \\
 65244 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 - 2) \times 4!)) \times (F(4))! \\
 65247 &:= -(((F(6) + 5)) \times (F((2 \times 4) - 7!))) \\
 65268 &:= (6 \times (((5! / (-2)) - F(6)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 65273 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times ((2 + 7!) - F(F(3!)))) \\
 65274 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5! / 2) + (7))) \times (F(4))! \\
 65277 &:= (((F(6))! + (-5) \times (2 - 7!)) - F(F(7))) \\
 65280 &:= (((F(6) \times 5!) \times 2) \times F((8 + 0!))) \\
 65287 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times ((5 + 2)!)) - 8!) - F(F(7))) \\
 65303 &:= -((F((F(6) + 5))) - ((3 + 0!)^{F(3)})) \\
 65313 &:= (((-((F(F(F(6))) - 5!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + 1) \times (-3)) \\
 65316 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5! / F(3))) \times (1 \times 6)) \\
 65324 &:= (F(6) - ((5! + (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2))) \times F(4))) \\
 65325 &:= (((F(6))! - 5!) / F(3!)) \times F((2 + 5)) \\
 65328 &:= (6 \times (-(((5! / F(3)) - 2) + F(F(8)))) \\
 65333 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 5!) \times 3!) + F((3! + F(3!)))) \\
 65334 &:= (6! + (F((5 + 3!)) \times ((3!)! + (F(4))!)) \\
 65335 &:= (((F(6))! / (-5!)) - ((F(F(F(3!))) \times (-3!)) + (5))) \\
 65337 &:= (-(((F(6))! + 5!)) - (F(F(3!)) \times (3 - 7!))) \\
 65338 &:= (((F(6))! / (-5!)) - F(3)) + (3! \times F(F(8))) \\
 \\
 65340 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 0 \\
 65341 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 1 \\
 65342 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 2 \\
 65343 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 3 \\
 65344 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 4 \\
 65345 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 5 \\
 65346 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 6 \\
 65347 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 7 \\
 65348 &:= -F(6)! / 5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}65349 &:= -F(6)!/5! + F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! + 9 \\65354 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((5! - (F(3!))!)/(-5)) + F(4!))) \\65358 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - 53) \times -((5 - 8)))! \\65364 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5!/F(3)) - F(6))) \times (F(4)!)) \\65369 &:= (F((6 + 5)) + (((F(3!))!/F(F(6))) \times F(9))) \\65373 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((5 \times (3!))! + F(F(7))) - 3!)) \\65374 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - ((5! \times (3!))! + (-7!) \times F(F(4)))))) \\65376 &:= ((F(6))! + ((5 - F((3! + F(7)))) \times (-6))) \\65377 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times ((F(3) + 7!) - F(7))) \\65378 &:= ((-((6^5)) \times (3! - F(7))) + F(F(8))) \\65379 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times 3!) - ((F(F(7)) + F(9)))) \\65384 &:= (((((F(6))!/5) + 3!) + F(F(8))) + F(4!)) \\65388 &:= (6 \times (((5!/(-3)) + F(F(8))) - 8)) \\65389 &:= -((F((F(6) + 5))) - (3! \times (F(F(8)) - 9)))) \\65392 &:= (((F(6)^5) - (F(3!) \times 9)) \times 2) \\65394 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((-5!) \times (F(3!) - F(9))) - (F(4)!)) \\65397 &:= (-6 + (F((5 + F(3))) \times (-9 + 7!))) \\65406 &:= ((6 \times F((-5) + 4!)) + (F(06))!) \\65407 &:= ((6 \times ((-5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - 0!) - F(F(7)) \\65408 &:= -(((F(6) + 5!) - (4^08))) \\65413 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times (F(4)!)) - (F(13))) \\65415 &:= (((F(6)^5) \times F(F(4))) + (-1 - 5!)) \\65416 &:= (((F(6)^5) \times F(F(4))) - (-((1 - 6)))!) \\65422 &:= ((6 - 5!) + (4^{F(F(2+2)!})) \\65424 &:= F(6) - 5! + 4^{2 \times 4} \\65425 &:= (((((F(6))! \times (-5))/F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(25)) \\65430 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) + ((4^{F(3!)} - 0!)) \\65431 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) + (4^{F(3! \times 1)})) \\65432 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) + ((4^{F(3!)} + F(2))) \\65433 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) + ((4^{F(3!)} + F(3))) \\65434 &:= ((-6) - 5!) + ((4^{F(3!)} + (4!))) \\65436 &:= (((F(6) \times (-5)) + F((4! - 3))) \times 6) \\65437 &:= ((F(6) - 5!) + ((4^{F(3!)} + F(7)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}65438 &:= ((F(6) - 5!) + (-((F(4))!) \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(8)))))) \\65442 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times 5!) - F(4)) \times (4! + 2)) \\65443 &:= ((-F((6 + 5))) + F((4! + F(4))))/3 \\65444 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (5!/F(4))) \times (F(4))!) + F((F(4))!)) \\65445 &:= ((F(6))! + (((5! - (F((F(4))!))!)/(-F((F(4))!))) \times 5)) \\65446 &:= (((6 - 5!) + 4!) + (4^{F(6)})) \\65448 &:= (((F(6) - 5!) + 4!) + (4^8)) \\65454 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5 + (F(F(4))^5))) \times (F(4))!) \\65455 &:= ((F(6) + (5)) \times (((F(F(4)) + (5)))! - (5))) \\65456 &:= (((((F(6))!/5) - F(F(4))) + 5!) \times F(6)) \\65456 &:= (((((F(6))!/5) - F(F(4))) + 5!) \times F(6)) \\65463 &:= ((-(65) + (4^{F(6)})) - F(3!)) \\65464 &:= (((F(6)^5) - ((F(4))! \times 6)) \times F(F(4))) \\65466 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 + 4!) + (6))) \times 6) \\65467 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times (F(4))!) + (-(6) - F(F(7)))) \\65469 &:= (-((F(6) - (5))) + ((F(4))! \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(9)))) \\65472 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) \times (F(4))!) - (F(F(7)) + F(2))) \\65473 &:= (((((6! + 5!) + F(4)) \times F(F(7)))/3) \\65474 &:= (((((F(6)^5) - 4!) - (7)) \times F(F(4))) \\65475 &:= ((F(6))! - ((-((5 + 4) + 7!) \times (-5))) \\65476 &:= (((F(6) + (5)) \times (-(4) + 7!)) + F(6)) \\65477 &:= (((F(6) \times (-5)) - F(4)) + (7! \times F(7))) \\65478 &:= (((((6! \times 5) - (F(4))!) \times 7) + 8!) \\65480 &:= ((F(6))! - (5 \times (F((F(4))!) - ((8 - 0!)!))) \\65481 &:= -(((F(6) + (5)) \times (F(4) - ((8 - 1!)!))) \\65482 &:= (((-((F(6)^5)) + (F(4))!) + (F(8))) \times (-2)) \\65484 &:= (((((F(6) + 5!)/(-4)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4))!) \\65493 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(F((5 + F(4)))) - F(9)) \times 3!)) \\65494 &:= (((((F(6)^5) \times F(F(4))) - F(9)) - F((F(4))!)) \\65495 &:= ((F(6))! + ((5 - (-((F(F(4)) - 9))!)) \times (-5))) \\65498 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (5)) + ((F(4))! \times (-(F(9)) + F(F(8)))))) \\65499 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (5! \times ((F(F(4))^9) + F(9)))) \\65505 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) + (0 - 5!)) \\65506 &:= (-((6 \times 5)) + ((5 - 0!)^{F(6)}))\end{aligned}$$

$$65507 := (((((6 + (5/5))))! - 0!) \times F(7))$$

$$65520 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 0$$

$$65521 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 1$$

$$65522 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 2$$

$$65523 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 3$$

$$65524 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 4$$

$$65525 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 5$$

$$65526 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 6$$

$$65527 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 7$$

$$65528 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 8$$

$$65529 := (F(6) + 5) \times (5 + 2)! + 9$$

$$65531 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (5!/5)) \times 3!) - 1)$$

$$65540 := ((F(F(6)) \times ((5^5) - 4)) - 0!)$$

$$65545 := ((F(6))! - ((-5) - ((5 + F(F(4))))!) \times 5))$$

$$65547 := ((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) + ((F(4))! \times (-F(7))))$$

$$65548 := -(((F((6!/5!)) + 5!) - ((F(4))! \times F(F(8)))))$$

$$65561 := ((F(F(F(6))) - 5!) - (-5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 1)))$$

$$65563 := (-((F((F(6) + (5))) - 5!)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3!))$$

$$65564 := (((F(F(F(6))) \times 5) - 5!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(4))!))$$

$$65568 := (6 \times (((5!/(-5)) + (6)) + F(F(8))))$$

$$65574 := ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5 + 5) + 7)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$65575 := (((F(6) + (5)) \times (-5 + 7!)) + 5!)$$

$$65576 := (((F(6))! + (((5 + 5))! \times F(7)))/6!)$$

$$65577 := -((F((6!/5!)) - ((5 + 7!) \times F(7))))$$

$$65579 := ((F(6))! - ((-5) \times (5 + 7!) - F(9)))$$

$$65583 := (F(F(6)) \times (((5^5) - 8) + 3!))$$

$$65587 := ((6 \times ((5!/5) + F(F(8)))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$65590 := ((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - (F(9) + 0!))$$

$$65598 := (6 \times ((-5) - F((F(-((5 - 9))))!)) + F(F(8))))$$

$$65603 := ((F(6)^5) + ((F(F(F(6))) - 0!) \times 3))$$

$$65604 := (((F(6)^5) + F((F(6) + 0!))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$65622 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - ((2 + 2)!))$$

$$65624 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6) - (-2 + 4!))$$

$$\begin{aligned}65630 &:= ((F(6) \times (-5)) + (6 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!))) \\65631 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(3!) + 1)))) \\65632 &:= (((F(6)^5) + (F(6) \times 3!)) \times 2) \\65633 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (5^{F(6)-3})) + F(3!)) \\65634 &:= (((F(F(6)) + 5) \times (F(F(6)) + 3!)) + F(4!)) \\65635 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times 6) - (3! + 5)) \\65637 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times ((6 + 3) + 7!)) \\65638 &:= ((-((6 \times 5)) - F(6)) + (3! \times F(F(8)))) \\65639 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times ((-5) + F(6)))! - (3 + F(9))) \\ \\65640 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 0 \\65641 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 1 \\65642 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 2 \\65643 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 3 \\65644 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 4 \\65645 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 5 \\65646 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 6 \\65647 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 7 \\65648 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 8 \\65649 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-5 + F(6))!) \times F(4)! + 9 \\ \\65650 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - 5) \times 6) + (5 - 0!)) \\65652 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times ((-5) + F(6)))! - ((5 - F(2)))!) \\65656 &:= (((F(6))! - (5 - 6!)) / 5) \times F(6) \\65658 &:= (6 \times (((5! / F(6)) / (-5)) + F(F(8)))) \\65663 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times ((-5) + F(6)))! - (F(F(6)) - F(3!))) \\65665 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times ((-5) + F(6)))! - (6 + 5)) \\65666 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((5 + 6))! / 6!) - 6!) \\65667 &:= ((F(F(6)) - ((-5) - F(6)) \times 6!) \times 7) \\65670 &:= (6 \times (F(F((56/7))) - 0!)) \\65675 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times ((-5) + F(6)))! - F((7 - 5))) \\65676 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times ((6 + 7!) + 6)) \\65677 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times ((-5) + F(6)))! + (7/7)) \\65680 &:= ((F(6) - 5) + ((6 \times F(F(8))) + 0!)) \\65681 &:= (6 + ((((-5) + F(6)))! \times F(F(8))) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65682 &:= (6 + (((-5) + F(6))! \times F((F(8) \times F(2)))))) \\ 65683 &:= (6 + ((((-5) + F(6))! \times F(F(8))) + F(F(3)))) \\ 65684 &:= (6 + ((((-5) + F(6))! \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4)))) \\ 65685 &:= (F(6) + ((5! - (-6!) \times F(F(8))))/5!) \\ 65689 &:= -((F(F(6)) - ((((-5) + F(6))! \times F(F(8))) + F(9)))) \\ 65697 &:= (F(F(6)) + (((-5) + F(6))! \times F((F(9) - F(7)))))) \\ 65698 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 5) \times (-((6 - 9)!)) - 8) \\ 65700 &:= (6 \times ((5 + F(F((7 + 0!)))) - 0!)) \\ 65702 &:= (F(F(F((6!/5!)))) + ((F(F(7)) + 0!)^2)) \\ 65703 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 5) \times (7 - 0!)) - 3) \\ 65704 &:= (((F(F(6)) + 5!) \times F(F(7)) - 0!) \times F(F(4))) \\ 65709 &:= ((6 \times F(F((-5) + F(7)))) - (0! - F(9))) \\ 65714 &:= (F(6) + ((5 + F(F((7 + 1)))) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 65715 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times (7! + 15)) \\ 65724 &:= ((F(6) + F((-5) + (F(7) \times 2))) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 65727 &:= (F((F(6) + 5)) - (F(7) \times (2 - 7!))) \\ 65728 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times (7! + ((2 \times 8)))) \\ 65730 &:= (6 \times (F(F((-5) + F(7)))) + (F(3!) + 0!)) \\ 65733 &:= (((6 + F(F((-5) + F(7)))) \times 3!) + F(F(3!))) \\ 65734 &:= ((F(F(6)) - 5) + ((7 + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 65736 &:= (((((F(6))! + 5!) \times F(7))/F(3!)) + F(F(6))) \\ 65737 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (-5) + F(7)) \times 3!) + F(7)) \\ 65739 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5 + 7)) \times 3!) - 9) \\ 65740 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((-5) \times (-F(7) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 0!)) \\ 65741 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (-5) \times (-F(7) - F(F(F(((4 - 1)!)))))) \\ 65742 &:= (6 \times (((5 + 7) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - F(2)) \\ 65743 &:= -((((F(F(6)) + 5) - F(F(7))) - (4^{F(3!)})) \\ 65744 &:= ((F(F(6)) - 5) \times (F(7) + (4^{F(4!)})) \\ 65745 &:= ((F(6))! - (-5) \times (7! + 45)) \\ 65747 &:= (((F(6) + 5) \times 7!) - (F(4))! + F(F(7))) \\ 65749 &:= (((((F(6))! + 5!) \times F(7))/F((F(4))!)) + F(9)) \\ 65753 &:= (F((F(6) + 5)) - (-7!) \times F((5 + F(3)))) \\ 65754 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F(((5 \times 7)/5))) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 65760 &:= F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$65761 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 1$$

$$65762 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 2$$

$$65763 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 3$$

$$65764 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 4$$

$$65765 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 5$$

$$65766 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 6$$

$$65767 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 7$$

$$65768 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 8$$

$$65769 := F(6)! - 5! \times (-F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) + 9$$

$$65774 := (((F(F(6)) - (-5 \times 7!)) + F(F(7))) + (F((F(4))!)))!$$

$$65780 := ((F(6) + 5) \times ((7! + F(8)) - 0!))$$

$$65783 := (65 - ((7 + F(F(8))) \times (-3!)))$$

$$65784 := (((6 + 5) + 7) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4))!$$

$$65787 := -(((6!/5!) - ((7! + F(8)) \times F(7))))$$

$$65788 := (-((F(6) - 5!) + ((7 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(8))))$$

$$65793 := ((F(6) + 5) \times (7! + F(F((9 - 3))))$$

$$65794 := (-((F(F(F(6))) + 5!) + (7 \times (F(9) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))))$$

$$65802 := ((6 + 5!) + (F(F(8)) \times ((0! + 2)!))$$

$$65804 := ((F(6) + 5!) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(04))!))$$

$$65808 := ((6!/5!) \times (F(F(8)) + (0! + F(8))))$$

$$65814 := ((6!/5!) \times (F(F(8)) + (-1 + 4!)))$$

$$65817 := ((F(F(6)) + 5!) + (F(F(8)) \times (-1 - 7)))$$

$$65820 := ((6!/5) + (F(F(8)) \times ((2 + 0!)!))$$

$$65823 := ((F(F(6)) + 5!) + ((F(F(8)) + F(2)) \times 3!))$$

$$65824 := (6! - (((5^8) + F(2))/(F(4))!))$$

$$65825 := ((6 \times (5 + F(F(8)))) - (F(2) - 5!))$$

$$65831 := (((F(F(6)) + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 3!) - 1$$

$$65833 := (((F(F(6)) + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 3!) + F(F(3))$$

$$65834 := (((F(F(6)) + 5) + F(F(8))) \times 3!) + F(F(4))$$

$$65835 := ((F(6))! - ((-5 \times F(8)) \times (3^5)))$$

$$65836 := (-((F(6) - 5!) + ((F(F(8)) + F(3!)) \times 6))$$

$$65844 := (((F(F(6)) + 5) + F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) \times (F(4))!$$

$$65845 := ((6 \times ((5 + F(F(8))) + (4!))) - (5))$$

$$65846 := ((F(F(6)) + 5) + ((F(F(8)) + (4!)) \times 6))$$

$$\begin{aligned}65848 &:= (((6 \times 5) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4))!) - 8) \\65849 &:= ((F(6))! + (((-5) + F(F(8))) \times F(F((F(4))!))))/9) \\65850 &:= (6 \times ((5 + F(F(8))) + ((5 - 0!)!)) \\65854 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) + ((5! + 8) \times (5! - ((F(4))!)))) \\65856 &:= (((6! + 5!) + 8!)/5) \times F(6) \\65856 &:= (((6! + 5!) + 8!)/5) \times F(6) \\65860 &:= (F((6 + 5)) \times ((F(8) + 6!) - 0!)) \\65864 &:= (((6 \times 5) + F(F(8))) \times 6) + F((F(4))!) \\65873 &:= ((6 \times (-5) + F(F(8)))) + (F(F(7)) - 3!) \\65874 &:= (((F(F(6)) + 5) + F(F(8))) + 7) \times (F(4))! \\65877 &:= (((F(6))!/5!) + (F(8) + (7! \times F(7)))) \\65880 &:= ((6!/5!) \times (F(F(8)) + F((8 + 0!)))) \\65884 &:= ((F(6) \times (5 + F(8))) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(4))!)) \\65886 &:= (((F(6))!/5!) + ((F(F(8)) - (F(8))) \times 6)) \\65893 &:= ((F(6) + 5) + ((F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times 3!)) \\65904 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((5 + F(9)) - 0!)) \times (F(4))! \\65928 &:= (6 \times ((F(F((F(-((5 - 9))))))!) \times 2) + F(F(8))) \\65933 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5! - 9!)/3))/F(3)) \\65934 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((5! + 9)/3)) \times (F(4))! \\65936 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (5! + F((9 \times F(3)))) \times F(6)) \\65938 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times 9)) \times 3!) - 8) \\65940 &:= (6 \times (((5 \times 9) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 0!)) \\65943 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (5 \times 9)) \times (F(4))!) - 3) \\65944 &:= (((F(6))^5 + (F(9) \times (F(4))!)) \times F(F(4))) \\65946 &:= ((6 \times F((-5) + (9 \times F(4)))) - (F(6))! \\65948 &:= ((F((6!/5!)) \times F(9)) + ((F(4))! \times F(F(8)))) \\65949 &:= ((F(F(6)) + ((F(-((5 - 9))))!) \times F((F(F(4)) + 9))) \\65962 &:= ((F(6) + 5) \times (F(9) + ((F(6) - F(2))!)) \\65963 &:= (F((F(6) + 5))) + ((9 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3!) \\65964 &:= (((6 + 5!) - F(9)) \times (6! - F(4))) \\65968 &:= -(((F(6) - 5!) \times (F((9 + 6)) - F(8))) \\65976 &:= ((6 \times (5 + F((9 + F(7)))) - (F(6))! \\66006 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F(((F(6) + 0!) + 0!)) \times 6) \\66024 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (60 - 2)) \times (F(4))! \\66030 &:= (6 \times ((60 + F(F(F(3)))) - 0!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}66033 &:= (((F(F(F(6)))) + 60) \times 3!) - 3) \\66034 &:= (((F(F(F(6)))) + 60) \times 3!) - F(F(4)) \\66035 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - ((0! + (-3 \times 5!))) \\66036 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + 60) \times -(3 - 6))! \\66038 &:= ((F(F(6)) + ((6! + 0!)) \times F((3 + 8))) \\66042 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + 0!) - (((F(4))!)! / (-2))) \\66043 &:= (-6) + ((F(F((F(6) - 0!))) + (4!)^{F(3)}) \\66044 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 60) \times (F(4))!) + F((F(4))!)) \\66047 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - 0!) + F((F(F(4)) \times 7))) \\66053 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + F(-(0! - (5 \times 3)))) \\66054 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6)) \times F(-(0! - (5)))))) \times (F(4))! \\66059 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + 0!) + (F((5 + 9)))) \\66066 &:= (((6! / F(6)) + 0!) \times (6! + (6))) \\66066 &:= (((6! / F(6)) + 0!) \times (6! + (6))) \\66074 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F((0! + F(7)))))) + F(F((F(4))!)) \\66084 &:= (((F(6) + (60)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4))! \\66108 &:= (6 \times ((6! / 10) + F(F(8)))) \\66138 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + 1)) + (3! \times F(F(8)))) \\66142 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F(F((1 + (F(4))!))) \times 2)) \\66157 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - (1 - 5!)) - F(F(7))) \\66159 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((6! - 1) \times (-5))) \times 9) \\66163 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - ((F(F((1 + 6))) - 3!))) \\66164 &:= ((F(6) \times 61) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (F(4))!)) \\66175 &:= (6! + (F((6 + 1)) \times (7! - (5)))) \\66198 &:= (6! + (6 \times ((1 - F(9)) + F(F(8)))) \\66204 &:= ((F(6))! - ((6^2) \times (0! - ((F(4))!)!)) \\66216 &:= (((6! / F(6)) + F(21)) \times 6) \\66227 &:= (6! + (F((F(6) - F(2))) \times -(F(2) - 7!))) \\66235 &:= (((6! / F(6)) + 2) \times (3!)! - (5)) \\66237 &:= -(((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(F(6)) + 2))) - (F(F(3!)) \times 7!)) \\66238 &:= (((6! \times (6^2)) - F(3)) + 8!) \\66239 &:= (((F(6) + 6!)^2 / F(3!)) - 9) \\66240 &:= 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 0 \\66241 &:= 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$66242 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 2$$

$$66243 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 3$$

$$66244 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 4$$

$$66245 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 5$$

$$66246 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 6$$

$$66247 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 7$$

$$66248 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 8$$

$$66249 := 6! \times (F(F(6)) + 2) \times 4 + 9$$

$$66252 := (((-6) - (F(6))!) \times (-2)) - (5!^2)$$

$$66256 := 6! + (6 - 2 \times 5)^{F(6)}$$

$$66258 := (-6) \times ((F(F(6)) + (2 - 5!)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$66262 := ((6! + (6)) + ((2^{F(6)})^2))$$

$$66264 := (((6!/F(6)) + 2) \times 6!) + 4!$$

$$66272 := (6! + (F(6) \times ((2^{F(7)}) + 2)))$$

$$66274 := -((F(F(6)) + (((F(6))!/(-2)) + F(F(7))) - F(4!)))$$

$$66276 := ((F(F(6)) \times ((6^2) + 7!)) - (F(6))!)$$

$$66284 := (F((F(F(6)) - 6)) + (-2) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(4))!))$$

$$66318 := (6! - (6 \times (F((3! + 1)) - F(F(8)))))$$

$$66324 := ((F(F(F(6))) + ((6^3)/2)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$66332 := (((6!/F(6)) + F(3)) \times ((3!)! + F(2)))$$

$$66333 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3!))) \times 3) + ((3!)!))$$

$$66334 := ((F((6 + F(F(6)))) + F((3 \times 3!)))/F(4))$$

$$66336 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (F(6) + F(3))) \times 3!) + (6!))$$

$$66338 := (((F(6) + 6!)^{F(3)} + 3!)/8)$$

$$66342 := (6! - (-6) \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F(4)^2)))$$

$$66344 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(6)) \times 3! - 4) + ((F(4))!))$$

$$66345 := (6! - (F(F(6)) \times (-((F(3) + F(4))^5)))$$

$$66346 := (((6!/F(6)) + 3!) + (4^{F(6)}))$$

$$66347 := (((F(F(F(6))) - 6) \times 3!) + ((F(4))!) - F(7))$$

$$66348 := (((6 \times (6! + 3)) \times (F(4))!) + 8!)$$

$$66352 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(F(3!)) + (5)^2))$$

$$66353 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(6)) \times 3!) + (5 + 3!))$$

$$66354 := ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(6)))/(-3) + 5!)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$66355 := ((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((3! - 5!)))) - (5))$$

$$66356 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((3!)! - (5 \times F(6))))$$

$$66358 := ((6! - F(6)) - (3! \times (5 - F(F(8)))))$$

$$66360 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 0$$

$$66361 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 1$$

$$66362 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 2$$

$$66363 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 3$$

$$66364 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 4$$

$$66365 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 5$$

$$66366 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6$$

$$66367 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 7$$

$$66368 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 8$$

$$66369 := 6! + 6 \times (-3! + F(F(F(6)))) + 9$$

$$66374 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(6))! + (3 \times (7! - (4)))))$$

$$66375 := -((F(F(6)) - (6 \times (F((3 \times 7)) + 5!))))$$

$$66376 := (((F(6))! / (F(6) - 3)) + F(F(7))) \times F(6)$$

$$66377 := ((6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + ((3! \times F(7)))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$66378 := (-((F(6) - ((F(6) + 3) \times 7!))) + F(F(8)))$$

$$66381 := ((6! - F(F(6))) + (3! \times (F(F(8)) + 1)))$$

$$66382 := (6! - ((6 \times (F(3) - F(F(8)))) + 2))$$

$$66383 := ((F(6))! + (((F(F(6)) \times (3!)!) + F(F(8))) - 3))$$

$$66384 := (((6! / 6) - F(3)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4))!$$

$$66385 := ((6! - (6)) + ((3! \times F(F(8))) - (5)))$$

$$66386 := (((6! \times F((6 + F(3)))) + F(F(8))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$66388 := (((6! \times F(F(6))) + F(3)) + F(F(8))) + 8!$$

$$66390 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 0$$

$$66391 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 1$$

$$66392 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 2$$

$$66393 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 3$$

$$66394 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 4$$

$$66395 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$66396 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 6$$

$$66397 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 7$$

$$66398 := 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66399 &:= 6 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(F(3!)) \times F(9) + 9 \\
 66401 &:= (6! + ((6 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0!)) - 1)) \\
 66402 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) + ((0! + 2)!)) \\
 66403 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (((F(4)! + 0!) + 3!)) \\
 66404 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) + F((F(04)!)) \\
 66405 &:= ((6! - F(F(6))) \times (-((4! + 0!) - 5!)) \\
 66408 &:= (6! + (6 \times (F(F(4)) + F(F(08)))) \\
 66413 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(4))) - (1 - 3!)) \\
 66414 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(4) + ((1 + 4)!))) \\
 66416 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) + (-1 + F(F(6)))) \\
 66417 &:= ((6! + F(F(6))) + ((F(4)! \times F(F((1 + 7)))))) \\
 66418 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) + (1 + F(8))) \\
 66420 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (4!)) + (((2 + 0!)!)) \\
 66423 &:= ((6! + F(F(6))) + ((F(4)! \times (F(2) + F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 66424 &:= -(((F(6) - (6! \times (-4))) \times (F(2) - 4!)) \\
 66426 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(6)) \times (F(4)! - F(2))) \times 6) \\
 66428 &:= (((F(6)! + F(F(F(6)))) - (((F(4)!))! + 2) \times (-F(8)))) \\
 66429 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) - ((F(2) - F(9)))) \\
 66430 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) + F((F(3!) + 0!)) \\
 66431 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 6) \times (F(4)!)) + (((3!) - 1)) \\
 66432 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)!))!) + (3!^2)) \\
 66433 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 6) \times (F(4)!)) + (F(F(3)) + 3!)) \\
 66434 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 6) \times (F(4)!)) + ((3!) + F(F(4)))) \\
 66435 &:= (F(F(6)) + (6 \times ((F(4) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5!)) \\
 66436 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(6)) \times (F(4)!)) + ((3!) - F(6))) \\
 66437 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(6)) \times (F(4)!)) + ((3!) - 7)) \\
 66438 &:= (6 \times (((F(F(6)) \times (F(4)!)) + F(F(3))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 66439 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4)^{3!}) + F(9))) \\
 66442 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(6)) \times (F(4)!)) + ((F(4)!))!) - 2) \\
 66443 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(6)) \times (F(4)! - F(F(F(4)))) + ((3!)!)) \\
 66444 &:= (6! + ((F(6) + F(F((4 + 4)))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 66445 &:= (-(6!) - (((F(F(6)) - (F((F(4)!))!)) / (-F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 66446 &:= (((F(6)^6) - F((4! + F(4)))) + (6!)) \\
 66447 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F(4) \times (4! + F(F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66448 &:= (6! + ((F(6) \times 4!) + (4^8))) \\
 66450 &:= (6 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(4))!)) + ((5! + 0!)))) \\
 66453 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(4))! + 5!)) \times 3!)) \\
 66455 &:= (-(6!) + (((F(6))! / (-F(4))) + (5)) \times (-5)) \\
 66456 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((6 + 4) + 5!)) \times 6) \\
 66457 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(4)) - (5^7)) \\
 66462 &:= ((-66) + F(4!)) + ((F(6))! / 2) \\
 66464 &:= ((-(F(6) \times F(6))) + F(4!)) + ((F(6))! / F(F(4))) \\
 66465 &:= (F(F(6)) + (6 \times ((F((F(4))!) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5!))) \\
 66468 &:= (6 \times (((F(F(6)) \times (F(4))!) + 6) + F(F(8)))) \\
 66469 &:= (((6! - F(F(F(6)))) / (-F(F(4)))) \times (-F(F(6)) - F(9))) \\
 66470 &:= (((6! - F(F(F(6)))) / (-F(F(4)))) \times F(7)) + 0! \\
 66472 &:= ((6 + ((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4))!)) \times F(7))) / 2) \\
 66473 &:= (((6! \times 6) \times (F(4))!) + F(F(7))) + (F(3))! \\
 66474 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(4))!)) - (-F(7) \times (F(4))!)) \\
 66475 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (F(6) \times ((F(F(4))^{F(7)} + 5!)))) \\
 66483 &:= (((6! + F(F(6))) + (F(4))!) \times F((8 + 3))) \\
 66484 &:= (6! - ((F(F(6))^{F(4)} - F((F(8) + (4)))))) \\
 66486 &:= (6! - (((F(F(6)) - (F(4))!) + F(F(8))) \times (-6))) \\
 66491 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((4! \times F(9)) - 1)) \\
 66492 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((4! \times F(9)) \times F(2))) \\
 66493 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((4! \times F(9)) + F(F(3)))) \\
 66494 &:= (((F(6))! / (6 - 4)) - F(9)) + F(4!) \\
 66495 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (F(9) + (5)))) \\
 66515 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5!)) - (1 - 5!)) \\
 66516 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (5! \times (1 + 6))) \\
 66522 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6)) + 5!)) \times (F((2 + 2))!)) \\
 66523 &:= (F((F(6) + F(6))) + ((5 - F(2))^{F(3)})) \\
 66524 &:= (((F(6) - (F(6))!) / (-F((5 - 2)))) + F(4!)) \\
 66528 &:= -(((6! - ((6^5) / 2)) \times F(8))) \\
 66534 &:= (((F(6))! / F((F(6) - (5)))) + 3!) + F(4!) \\
 66535 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (6! / 5)) \times 3!) - (5)) \\
 66537 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((5! + 3) \times 7)) \\
 66540 &:= 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 0
 \end{aligned}$$

$$66541 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 1$$

$$66542 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 2$$

$$66543 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 3$$

$$66544 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 4$$

$$66545 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 5$$

$$66546 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 6$$

$$66547 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 7$$

$$66548 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 8$$

$$66549 := 6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 5! + 4!) + 9$$

$$66564 := ((F(6))! - (((F(6) - 5))^{F(6)}) \times (-4))$$

$$66570 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (6^5)) \times F((7 + 0!)))$$

$$66573 := ((6! + F((F(F(6)) - 5))) \times (F(7) \times 3))$$

$$66574 := -((F(F(F(6))) + ((6! \times F((5 + F(7)))) / (-4!)))$$

$$66577 := (((F(F(F(6))) - (6! - 5)) \times 7) - (7!))$$

$$66588 := (6 \times (((6!/5) + 8) + F(F(8))))$$

$$66594 := ((F(F(F(6))) + ((6!/5) + 9)) \times (F(4))!)$$

$$66595 := ((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (5! + F(9)))) - (5))$$

$$66599 := -((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(F(6)) \times 5!) + F((F(9) - 9))))$$

$$66627 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((6! - 2) + F(F(7))))$$

$$66636 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((6!/3) + 6!))$$

$$66637 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((F(6) + 3!) + F(F(7))))$$

$$66647 := (6! + ((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(4))) + F(F(7))))$$

$$66648 := (((-6!) - F((F(6) + 6))) \times (-4!)) + 8!$$

$$66652 := ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F(6) \times (5! + 2)))$$

$$66654 := ((F(F(6)) \times (6 + (F(6) \times 5!))) + F(4!))$$

$$66674 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((6! \times (6 + 7)) + F(4!)))$$

$$66677 := ((F((66/6)) + 7!) \times F(7))$$

$$66684 := (((6!/F(6)) \times (6! + F(8))) - (F(4))!)$$

$$66685 := (((6!/F(6)) \times (6! + F(8))) - (5))$$

$$66688 := ((-6!) \times F(F(6))) - ((6! - F(F(8))) \times 8)$$

$$66690 := ((6! + F(F(6))) \times (6! / (9 - 0!)))$$

$$66717 := (F(F(6)) \times ((-F(6)) \times F(F(7))) + (1 + 7!))$$

$$66727 := ((6! \times (F(F(6)) + (72))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$66734 := (((F(6))! - (((F(6))! - F(F(7))) \times 3!)) / (-F(4)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66743 &:= (((6! + 6!) - F(F(7))) + (4^{F(3!)})) \\
 66744 &:= ((6! + (F(6) \times F(7))) \times (F(4)^4)) \\
 66745 &:= (((F(6))! - (F(F(6)) \times F(7)))/F(4)) \times 5) \\
 66759 &:= -(((F(F(6)) \times F(F(6))) - ((7! \times 5!)/9))) \\
 66773 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + (F((7 + 7)) + 3!)) \\
 66792 &:= ((6! + ((F(F(6))/7))!) \times 92) \\
 66795 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(6))) - (7! + (9!/(-5))) \\
 66824 &:= (((F(6) \times 6!) + F(F(8))) \times (F(2) + F(4))) \\
 66828 &:= (6 \times ((F(6) \times ((8/2))!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 66834 &:= (6 + (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(3!) \times 4!))) \\
 66840 &:= (F(6) \times ((6! \times F(8)) - F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!))) \\
 66864 &:= (6 \times ((6 + F(F(8))) + (F(6) \times 4!))) \\
 66873 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(6))) + ((8! + (F(7))!)/(F(3!)!)) \\
 66878 &:= ((6 - (F(6) \times F(F(8)))) - ((F(7))!/(-8!))) \\
 66894 &:= (-6) - (-6) \times (F(F(8)) + (F(9) \times (F(4))!)) \\
 66897 &:= (((6! \times 6!)/8) + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \\
 66906 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((6 \times F(9)) + 0!)) \times 6) \\
 66923 &:= (((F(6))! + (F(F(F(6))) \times (F(9) - F(2))))/3!) \\
 66933 &:= ((-6) - F(F(6))) + (93 \times (3!)!) \\
 66936 &:= (((F(6) - 6!) \times (-93)) + 6!) \\
 66939 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (6! \times ((F(9) \times 3) - 9))) \\
 66942 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(9)^{F(4)}) \times (-2)) \\
 66944 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + 6) - F((9 \times F(F(4)))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\
 66945 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - (-9) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) + 5!)) \\
 66947 &:= ((6! \times (69 + 4!)) - F(7)) \\
 66952 &:= -((F(6) - (6! \times (95 - 2)))) \\
 66954 &:= (-6) + (-6!) \times (-95 + F(F(4))) \\
 \\
 66960 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 0 \\
 66961 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 1 \\
 66962 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 2 \\
 66963 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 3 \\
 66964 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 4 \\
 66965 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 5 \\
 66966 &:= 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$66967 := 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 7$$

$$66968 := 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 8$$

$$66969 := 6! \times (F(6) \times 9 + F(F(6))) + 9$$

$$66976 := ((6! + 6!) + ((-9) + F(7))^{F(6)})$$

$$66984 := ((6! \times ((F(6) \times 9) + F(8))) + 4!)$$

$$66996 := ((F(6))! - (((F(6))!/9) - F(9)) \times (-6))$$

$$67026 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) - F((0! + 2)!)) \times 6)$$

$$67032 := ((F(6) + F((F(7) - 0!))) \times (F(F(3!))^2))$$

$$67038 := (6 \times ((F(F(7)) - (03)!) + F(F(8))))$$

$$67044 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) - (0! + (4)))) \times (F(4)!)$$

$$67053 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times (0! + (5))) - F(F(3!)))$$

$$67054 := (((6! - 70) \times 5!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$67056 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) - F(-(0! - (5)))) \times 6)$$

$$67062 := (6 \times (((F(F(7)) - 0!) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(2)))$$

$$67064 := (((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) - 0!))) \times 6) - 4)$$

$$67068 := (6 \times ((F(F(7)) - ((0 \times 6)!) + F(F(8))))$$

$$67072 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times (-0! - (7))) - 2)$$

$$67073 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times (-0! - (7))) - F(F(3)))$$

$$67075 := (F(6) - (F(7) \times ((0! - 7!) - 5!)))$$

$$67080 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 0$$

$$67081 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 1$$

$$67082 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 2$$

$$67083 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 3$$

$$67084 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 4$$

$$67085 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 5$$

$$67086 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 6$$

$$67087 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 7$$

$$67088 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 8$$

$$67089 := 6 \times (F(F(7)) + 0! + F(F(8))) + 9$$

$$67104 := ((-6) \times F(F(7))) \times ((-1 - 0!) \times 4!)$$

$$67115 := ((F(6))! + (F(F(7)) \times 115))$$

$$67194 := (-6) - (-(((7 + 1)!) + 9!)/(F(4)!))$$

- 67232 := $((F(6))! - (((F(F(7)) - F(2))^{F(3)})/(-2)))$
- 67235 := $(((((F(6))! + F((7 + F(2))))/3) \times 5)$
- 67236 := $(6 \times ((F(7) \times (-F(2) + F(F(3!)))) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 67244 := $((6! - ((7! - F(2)) \times (-4))) + F(4!))$
- 67245 := $((((6 \times 7!) \times 2) + F((4 \times 5)))$
- 67246 := $((((F(6))! + (7!)) + (2 \times (-F(4) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 67248 := $(6! + ((F(7) - 2) \times (F(4!) - 8!)))$
- 67252 := $((((F(6))! + (7!)) - (-2 \times F(F(F(((5 - 2)!))))))$
- 67264 := $((((F(6))! + (7!)) - (-2 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(4)!))))$
- 67268 := $((((F(6))! + (7!)) - (2 \times (-F(6) - F(F(8))))))$
- 67273 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times F(7)) - F((F(2) + ((7 - 3)!)))$
- 67277 := $-((F(F(6)) + ((7 \times 2) \times (-7!) + F(F(7))))))$
- 67284 := $((((6 \times F((F(7) - 2))) \times F(8)) \times (F(4)!))$
- 67307 := $((((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times 3!) - (0 - F(F(7))))$
- 67308 := $(6 \times ((F(7) \times F(F(3!))) - (0! - F(F(8))))$
- 67314 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) \times F(F(3!)))) \times (F((1 \times 4)!))$
- 67323 := $((((6 \times 7)^3) - F((-F(2) + F(F(3!))))))$
- 67324 := $((-((F(F(6)) + (7!)) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2))) \times 4)$
- 67325 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((7! - F(3))/2)) \times 5)$
- 67326 := $(6 \times (((F(7) \times F(F(3!))) + 2) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 67327 := $((((6! \times F(7)) - F((F(F(3!)) - 2))) \times F(7))$
- 67330 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((7!/F(3)))) \times (3! - 0!))$
- 67332 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) \times (((3!)/3) + 2)))$
- 67334 := $((((-6!) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(F(3)) - F(F(3!)))) + F(4!))$
- 67338 := $((((6! \times F(F(7)))/F(3!)) + F((3 \times 8)))$
- 67342 := $-((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(7)) \times F(3!)) \times (-42))))$
- 67343 := $(6 + (F(F(7)) \times ((F(F(3!)) - 4)^{F(3)}))$
- 67344 := $(((((6! \times F(F(7)))/F(3!)) + F(4!)) + (F(4)!))$
- 67345 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((7!/F(3)) + F(4))) \times 5)$
- 67346 := $(((((6! \times F(F(7)))/F(3!)) + F(4!)) + F(6))$
- 67347 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(7) + (F(3) \times F((4! - 7))))))$
- 67348 := $((-((F(6) + (7!/(-3)))) + ((F(4)! \times F(F(8))))$
- 67354 := $((((F(F(F(6))) + ((7!/F(3)))) \times 5) + (4!))$
- 67355 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((7!/F(3)) + (5))) \times 5)$
- 67356 := $((F(F(F(6))) + ((7 \times F(3!)) \times 5)) \times 6)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67360 &:= ((F(F(F(6)))/(-F(7))) \times ((3!)!/(-F(6) + 0!))) \\
 67368 &:= (F(6) \times ((F(F(7)) + (F(3!) \times F(F(6)))) \times F(8))) \\
 67380 &:= ((F(6))! - (-((7 - 3) \times F((F(8) - 0!)))) \\
 67382 &:= (((-6) + 7!) + F((F(3) + F(8)))) \times 2 \\
 67383 &:= ((6! + F((F(7) + 3))) + (F(F(8)) \times 3!)) \\
 67384 &:= (F(6) \times ((-((7!/F(3))) + F(F(8))) - F(4))) \\
 67392 &:= ((F(6) - (7!/3!)) \times (-9^2)) \\
 67394 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + (7!)) + (-((F(3) - 9)))! + F(4!)) \\
 67397 &:= (6! - ((-7!) - F((F(3) + 9))) \times F(7)) \\
 67398 &:= (6 \times ((F(F(7)) + (3! \times 9)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 67402 &:= (F(6) + ((7! + F((4! - 0!))) \times 2)) \\
 67404 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (7!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 0!) \times 4) \\
 67408 &:= (F(6) \times ((-7!/F(F(4))) + F(F(08)))) \\
 67416 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((7!/F(F(4))) - 1)) \times F(6)) \\
 67418 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (7!)) - ((F(4)!))! \times F(-((1 - 8)))) \\
 67424 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - ((7! - (4))/2)) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 67433 &:= (((F(6))! + F(F(7))) - ((-4) \times (F(3!)!)/3!)) \\
 67434 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times (F(4)! + ((3!)!/F(F(4)))) \\
 67435 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - (-7!/F(F(4)))) + F(F(3!))) \times 5) \\
 67436 &:= ((6! + F(7)) \times (F(4) + F((3 + F(6)))) \\
 67437 &:= (6 + (7 \times (((F(4)!))! + F(F(3!))) \times F(7))) \\
 67440 &:= ((-6) - (7!/F(4))) \times (-40) \\
 67443 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7))^{F(F(4))})) + (F(4!)/F(F(3!)))) \\
 67445 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times 7) + (F((F(4)!))!)/F(4)) \times 5) \\
 67447 &:= ((6! \times (F(7) + (F(4)⁴))) - F(F(7))) \\
 67448 &:= ((F(6) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(4)!)) + (4⁸)) \\
 67449 &:= (((6 \times F(F(7))) + F(4!)) + ((F(4)⁹))) \\
 67452 &:= (((F(6))! - F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (-5))/(-2))) \\
 67454 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (((7 \times F((F(4)!)) \times 5)^{F(F(4))}))) \\
 67456 &:= (((F(F(F(6)))/F(7)) \times (F((F(4)!)) + 5!)) - (F(6)!)) \\
 67457 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (7!)) + F((F(4)!)) + 5!) \times F(7)) \\
 67459 &:= (-F(F(6)) - (((7! + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 5!)/(-9))) \\
 67464 &:= ((F(6))! - (F(7) \times ((4! - 6!) \times F(4))) \\
 67469 &:= ((F(6))! + ((-7) + 4!) \times F((F(6) + 9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67473 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((7! + F(4!)) / (F(7) + 3))) \\
 67476 &:= (((67 + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + F(F(7))) \times 6) \\
 67476 &:= (((67 + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + F(F(7))) \times 6) \\
 67487 &:= ((-F(6)) - (F(7) \times (((F(4)!))! + (F(8)))))) \times (-7) \\
 67488 &:= (((((F(6))! \times (-F(7))) - F(4!)) / (-F(8))) + 8!) \\
 67494 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(7) \times 4!) - 9)) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 67536 &:= (67 \times ((5! + 3!) \times F(6))) \\
 67542 &:= ((6 + (7! \times (-5))) - (F(4!) \times (-2))) \\
 67544 &:= (((F(6) + (7! \times (-5))) + F(4!)) + F(4!)) \\
 67545 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(7)) \times (5 + (F(4)!)))) \times 5) \\
 67547 &:= (((F(6))! - F(7)) + (-5! \times ((F(4))! - F(F(7)))))) \\
 67548 &:= (((6! \times F(7)) / 5) + ((F(4))! \times F(F(8)))) \\
 67549 &:= -((F(F(6)) + (F(F(7)) \times (-5) \times (4! + F(9)))))) \\
 \\
 67560 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 0 \\
 67561 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 1 \\
 67562 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 2 \\
 67563 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 3 \\
 67564 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 4 \\
 67565 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 5 \\
 67566 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 6 \\
 67567 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 7 \\
 67568 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 8 \\
 67569 &:= F(6)! + F(F(7)) \times 5! - 6! + 9 \\
 \\
 67573 &:= ((F(6))! + (((F(F(7)) \times 5!) + F(7)) - 3!)) \\
 67584 &:= (((-6) + F(F(7))) \times 5!) + ((8! + 4!)) \\
 67594 &:= (((F(6))! - ((F(F(7)) \times (-5!)) - F(9))) - ((F(4))!))! \\
 67600 &:= (((6 + F(F(7))) + F(F(6)))^{0!+0!}) \\
 67616 &:= (6! + (F((F(7) + (6))) \times 16)) \\
 67624 &:= (((6 + F(F(7))) + F(F(6)))^2) + (4!) \\
 67638 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(7)) + ((6! \times 3!))) + 8!) \\
 67645 &:= (-6!) - ((F(F(7)) + ((F(6))! / F(4))) \times (-5)) \\
 67646 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((7! \times 6!) / (F(F(4))^6)) \\
 67663 &:= ((-6!) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(6) + (63)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67671 &:= (F(6) + ((F(F(7)) + (6!)) \times 71)) \\
 67684 &:= ((F(6) \times F(F(7))) + (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (4!)))) \\
 67689 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F(7)) \times (-6 - F(8))) + 9!) \\
 67693 &:= ((6! + F(7)) - (6! \times (-93))) \\
 67694 &:= (F(F(6)) + (-7) + (6! \times 94)) \\
 67734 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(7))) + ((7^3))) \times (F(4))!) \\
 67735 &:= ((6! - 7) \times ((F(7) + 3!) \times 5)) \\
 67743 &:= (-F(F(F(6)))) - (F(7) \times ((F(F(7)) \times F(F((F(4))!))) - F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 67764 &:= ((((-6) \times F(F(7))) - (7!)) + (F(6))!) \times F(F(4)) \\
 67767 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((7 \times F(F(7))) + (F(6))!) / F(7))) \\
 67768 &:= (((6! - F(7)) \times F(7)) - 6!) \times 8 \\
 67782 &:= (-6!) - (F(F(7)) \times ((7 \times F(8)) \times (-2))) \\
 67783 &:= (((6! - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7)))) \times F(8)) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 67794 &:= (((F(F(6)) + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(7)) + F(9))) - (4!)) \\
 67824 &:= (((((F(6))! \times 7) - F(F(8))) + 2) / 4) \\
 67826 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((78 + F(2)) \times 6!)) \\
 \\
 67830 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 0 \\
 67831 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 1 \\
 67832 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 2 \\
 67833 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 3 \\
 67834 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 4 \\
 67835 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 5 \\
 67836 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 6 \\
 67837 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 7 \\
 67838 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 8 \\
 67839 &:= F(F(6))! / (F(7)! \times 8! \times 3) + 9 \\
 \\
 67847 &:= (((6! \times F((-7) + F(8)))) / 4) - F(7) \\
 67866 &:= ((-6!) \times (F(F(7)) - 8)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(6)))) \\
 67872 &:= (((6! - F(7)) \times 8) \times (F(7) - F(2))) \\
 67896 &:= (((-6!) - F(F(7))) \times (-8 \times 9)) - (6!) \\
 67920 &:= -(((F(6))! - ((7 + 9) \times F(20)))) \\
 67924 &:= (-6!) - (((F(7))! / 9!) + F(2)) \times (-4) \\
 67932 &:= (((F(6) - 7!) \times (-9 \times 3)) / 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67933 &:= ((6! + F(7)) + ((-9!) - (F(3!)!)/(-3!)) \\
 67943 &:= (((-6!) + F((F(7) + 9))) \times 4) - F(F(3!)) \\
 67944 &:= (-6!) - (((F(7))!/9!) + (F(4)!) \times (-4)) \\
 67946 &:= (((6! + (7)) \times (F(9) + (4))) + (F(6))!) \\
 67956 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(F(7)) + ((9!/5!))) - F(F(6)))) \\
 67964 &:= ((F(((6 + 7) + 9)) - 6!) \times 4) \\
 67976 &:= ((-F(6)) \times F(F(7))) + (97 \times 6!) \\
 67977 &:= (((6! - (7)) + F(9)) \times F(7)) \times 7) \\
 67982 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 7) - ((9!/F(8))/2)) \\
 67986 &:= (6 \times (7! + (-9) \times (F(8) - 6!))) \\
 67993 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times F(7)) - (F((F(9) - 9)) - 3!)) \\
 68066 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - (-80) \times (6! - (6))) \\
 68196 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8))!/(19)!)) \times 6) \\
 68233 &:= (-((F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) - (2 \times ((3!)! - (F(3!)!))) \\
 68234 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) - F((8 - F(2)))) \times F(3)) + F(4!)) \\
 68236 &:= ((F(6))! - (((F(8) - F(23)) + 6!)) \\
 68240 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (((F(F(8)) \times 2) + F(4!)) + 0!)) \\
 68242 &:= ((((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 2) + F(4!)) - 2) \\
 68243 &:= ((((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 2) + F(4!)) - F(F(3)) \\
 68244 &:= ((((-F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times (-2 - 4)) + F(4!)) \\
 68246 &:= (-F(6)) - (((F(F(8)) \times (-2)) - F(4!)) + 6) \\
 68247 &:= (-6) - (((F(F(8)) \times (-2)) - F(4!)) + 7) \\
 68249 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(F(8)) - 2) + F(4!)) - 9) \\
 68254 &:= (-6) + ((F(F(8)) \times F(-(2 - 5))) + F(4!)) \\
 68255 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) + F((-((F(2) - (5))))!)) - (5)) \\
 68257 &:= (-((6! - 8!)) + F((2 \times 5) + F(7))) \\
 68259 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(8)) - F(2))) + F((-((5 - 9))))!) \\
 \\
 68260 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 0 \\
 68261 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 1 \\
 68262 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 2 \\
 68263 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 3 \\
 68264 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 4 \\
 68265 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 5 \\
 68266 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68267 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 7 \\
 68268 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 8 \\
 68269 &:= F(F(F(6))) + F(F(8)) + F((-2 + 6)!) + 9 \\
 \\
 68273 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(((8/2)!) + F(7)))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 68274 &:= (F(F(6)) - (((F(F(8)) \times (-2)) + 7) - F(4!))) \\
 68275 &:= (((-6) + 8!) + F(2)) + (F(F(7)) \times 5!) \\
 68284 &:= (((F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 2) + 8) + F(4!) \\
 68294 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(2) \times F(9))) + F(4!))) \\
 68304 &:= (((-6) - 8!)/3!) + F((0! + 4!)) \\
 68321 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F(3!))^2))) - 1) \\
 68323 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F(3!))^2))) + F(F(3))) \\
 68324 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(8)) + ((F(3!)^2) + F(4!))) \\
 68328 &:= ((6! - (F(8)^3)) \times (F(2) \times (-8))) \\
 68334 &:= ((-((6! - (F(8)^3))) \times F(3!)) + (F(4)!)) \\
 68336 &:= ((-((6! - (F(8)^3))) + F(F(3))) \times F(6)) \\
 68343 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}))) \times (F(4)!)) + F(F(3!))) \\
 68344 &:= (((((F(6)!) + F(F(8))) - F(3!))/F(4)) \times 4) \\
 68355 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (F(8) \times (35 + 5!))) \\
 68364 &:= (((F(6)!/F(8)) - F(F(3!))) \times (6^{F(F(4))})) \\
 68367 &:= (((F(6)!) + F((F(8) + F(3)))) - F((F(6) + (7)))) \\
 68370 &:= (-6!) + (F((8 \times F(3))) \times 70) \\
 68375 &:= (((6 + 8!)/(-3)) - F(F(7))) \times (-5) \\
 68376 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (((8 + 3!) \times F(F(7))) - 6)) \\
 68394 &:= ((-6) + 8!) - (-39 \times ((F(4)!))!) \\
 68395 &:= -((F((F(6) + (8 + 3))) + (9!/(-5)))) \\
 68404 &:= ((F((-6) + F(8))) - F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!))) \times (-4)) \\
 68405 &:= (((6! + 8!)/F(4)) + 0!) \times 5 \\
 68414 &:= ((6 - (F(F(8)) \times (-4! + 1)))/4) \\
 68425 &:= (((6! - 8!)/F(4)!) + F(25)) \\
 68428 &:= (((F(6) \times F(8)) + F(4!)) - (-2 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 68434 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) \times (3!)!)/4)) \\
 68435 &:= (((((F(6)!) + F(8))) + ((F(4)!))!)/3) \times 5 \\
 68438 &:= (((6 \times F((F(8) - 4))) \times 3!) + F(F(8))) \\
 68439 &:= (((F(6)!) - F(F(8))) \times F(4)) - ((3^9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68443 &:= -(((F(F(6)) - F((F(8) + (4)))) + (F(4)^{F(3)}))) \\
 68444 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(F(8)) + (F(4)!) / 4) \times F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 68445 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F(F(8))) / F(F(4))) - F(4!)) - 5! \\
 68449 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) + F(4!))) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times 9)) \\
 68450 &:= (((6 + F(F(8))) / F((F(4)!)) \times 50) \\
 68466 &:= (6 \times ((F(F(8)) + (4!)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 68467 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) - (-4!) \times F(F(6)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 68477 &:= ((6! \times F(8)) - ((4 - F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 68487 &:= (((-((6! - 8!)) \times F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) \\
 68488 &:= (-((F(6) - 8!)) - (((4!)! / (F(8)!)) - 8!)) \\
 68493 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) + F(4!))) + F(F((9 - F(3)))))) \\
 68495 &:= ((6! + F((8/4))) \times 95) \\
 68496 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8) \times 4!) - F(9))) \times 6) \\
 68507 &:= ((-6) + 8!) - (-((5! + 0!) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 68513 &:= ((F(-((F(6) - F(8)))) \times (5! + 1)) + (F(3)!)) \\
 68543 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) - 5) + ((F(4)!)^{3!})) \\
 68546 &:= (((F(6)!) + F(F(8))) - ((5! \times 4!) \times (-6))) \\
 68548 &:= ((6 \times F(F(8))) + ((5! \times 4!) - 8)) \\
 68552 &:= ((6 + F(F(8))) + ((5! + 5!)^2)) \\
 68554 &:= ((F(6) + F(F(8))) + ((5! \times 5!) \times 4)) \\
 68556 &:= (((6! + F(F(8))) - ((5! + 5!))) \times 6) \\
 68586 &:= (((F(6) \times (-8)) \times 5!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 68586 &:= (((F(6) \times (-8)) \times 5!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 68657 &:= (((F(6)!) + (F((8 + 6)))) + (5! \times F(F(7)))) \\
 68658 &:= (6 \times ((F((8 + 6)) + 5!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 68664 &:= (-6!) - (-F(8) \times (6! + F((-6) + 4!))) \\
 68694 &:= (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (-((6! - 9!) / ((F(4)!)))))) \\
 68704 &:= (((F(6)!) - (F(8) \times F(7))) + F(-((0! - 4!))) \\
 68723 &:= (((F(6)!) - (F(8))) - F(F(7))) + (F(23)) \\
 68724 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times 2)) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 68725 &:= (((F(6)!) - (F(8))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-2 - 5!))) \\
 68734 &:= (F(6) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(3)) + F(4!))) \\
 68736 &:= (-6!) - ((F(F(8)) + (7! / F(3!))) \times (-6)) \\
 68738 &:= (((-6) + 8!) - F(F(7))) + F((F(3) + F(8))) \\
 68744 &:= (((F(6)!) + F(F(8))) - F(F(7))) + F((4! - F(F(4))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68752 &:= ((6 + 8!) - (F(F(7)) \times (-(5! + 2)))) \\
 68754 &:= (((6! - (F(8) \times 7)) \times 5!) - (F(4)!)) \\
 68755 &:= (((6! - (F(8) \times 7)) \times 5!) - (5)) \\
 68760 &:= ((6! - (F(8) \times 7)) \times ((6 - 0!)!)) \\
 68784 &:= (((6! + F(8)) - 7!) \times (8 - 4!)) \\
 68832 &:= -(((F(6) - (8!/F(8))) \times (3!^2))) \\
 68833 &:= ((6! \times 88) - (F(F(F(3!)))/(-F(3)))) \\
 68834 &:= (((6! \times 8) + F((F(8) + F(3)))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 68844 &:= (((6! + F(F(8))) - (8 \times 4!)) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 68845 &:= (((F(6)! + F((8 + 8)))/F(4)) \times 5) \\
 68854 &:= (((F(6)! - F(F(8))) + (8! - 5!)) - ((F(4)!)!)) \\
 68887 &:= ((6! \times (8 + 88)) - F(F(7))) \\
 68907 &:= -(((F(6)! - ((F(F(8)) \times (9 + 0!)) - F(F(7)))))) \\
 68913 &:= ((6! + F(8)) \times (91 + F(3))) \\
 68934 &:= (((6! + F(8)) \times 93) + F(F((F(4)!))) \\
 68943 &:= (((F(6)! + F(F(8))) - F(9)) + F((4! - F(3)))) \\
 68944 &:= (((F(6)!)/(-8)) + ((F(9) \times F((F(4)!))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 68946 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (((F(F(8)) - F(9)) + F(4!)) + (6!))) \\
 68947 &:= -((F(F(6)) + (((-8) \times F(9)) - 4!) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 68948 &:= ((F(6)! + ((F(F(8)) \times (-F(9)))/F((F(4)! - (F(8)))))) \\
 68953 &:= -(((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) + ((9 - 5!) \times (3!)!)) \\
 68956 &:= (((F(6)! - (F(8))) + F((F(9) - (5 + 6)))) \\
 68958 &:= ((6 + F(8)) \times (F(9) + (5! \times F(8)))) \\
 68962 &:= (((-6) + 8!) - 9) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)) \\
 68964 &:= (((F(6)! + ((F(8) - F(9)))) + F((F(F(6)) + F(F(4)))))) \\
 68971 &:= ((-6) + 8!) + F(((9 + F(7)) + 1)) \\
 68973 &:= ((6! \times 89) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 68974 &:= (((F(6)! + F((F(8) + (9 - 7)))) - F(4)) \\
 68976 &:= ((F(6) + 8) \times ((-9) + 7!) - 6!) \\
 68977 &:= ((F(6)! + (F(((8 \times 9) - (7 \times 7)))))) \\
 68983 &:= ((F(((6 + 8) + 9)) + 8!) + 3!) \\
 68994 &:= (((F((6 + 8)) \times F(9)) \times 9) - F(4!)) \\
 69024 &:= ((6 + 90) \times (-(F(2)) + ((F(4)!)!)) \\
 69032 &:= (((F(6)! + F((9 + 0!))) + F((F(F(3!)) + 2))) \\
 69035 &:= (((-6) - 9!) + F((0! + F(F(3!)))))/(-5)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 69046 := ((69 + F(-((0! - 4!)))) + (F(6))!)
 69055 := -(((F(6))! - ((F(9) + 0!) × (5⁵))))
 69088 := ((F(6) × F(9)) × (F(F(-((0! - 8)))) + (F(8))))
 69106 := (-(((F(6))! + F(9))) + (10 × F(F(F(6))))))
 69124 := (((F(F(6)) + 9!)/F(F(((1 + 2)!))) × 4)
 69130 := (-((F(6))!) + ((9 + 1) × (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!)))
 69134 := (((F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1)) - (F(3!))!) - (F(4))!)
 69135 := (((F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1)) - (F(3!))!) - (5))
 69136 := (F(6) × ((F(9) × F(13)) + 6!))
 69138 := ((F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1)) - (F(3) + 8!))

 69140 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 0
 69141 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 1
 69142 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 2
 69143 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 3
 69144 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 4
 69145 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 5
 69146 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 6
 69147 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 7
 69148 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 8
 69149 := F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1) - F(F(4))! + 9

 69164 := ((F(F(F(6))) × (9 + 1)) - (((F(6))! - (4!))))
 69173 := (((((F(6))!/9) - 1) × F(7)) + F(F(F(3!))))
 69186 := (((((F(6))!/9) × F(-((1 - 8)))) + F(F(F(6))))
 69204 := ((-F(F(6))) - (9!/F(F(((2 + 0!)!)))) × (-4))
 69228 := (((((F(6))! - F(F((9 - 2)))) × 2) - F(F(8)))
 69237 := (F(F(6)) × ((F((9 × 2)) + 3!) - 7))
 69246 := ((F(F(F(6))) × (-9)) + (F(F((F(2) + (F(4))!))) × 6!))
 69247 := (((F(F(F(6))) × (-9)) + F(2)) - (((F(4))!)! × (-F(F(7))))))
 69258 := (F(F(6)) × (F(9) × ((-2) + 5!) - F(8)))
 69263 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((9²) × 6!) - 3))
 69264 := (F(F(F(6))) + (((9²) × 6!) - F(F(4))))
 69266 := (F(F(F(6))) + ((F((9 + 2)) - F(6)) × 6!))
 69273 := (((6! × (9²)) + (7)) + F(F(F(3!))))

$$\begin{aligned} 69277 &:= (((F(6) + 9)^2) + 7!) \times F(7) \\ 69288 &:= (F(6) \times ((9!/2)/F(8)) + F(8)) \\ 69324 &:= (6 \times (F(9) - (3!! \times (-2^4)))) \\ 69330 &:= (6 \times ((F(9 + 3!)) + F(F(3!)))) - 0!) \\ 69333 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F((9 + 3!))) \times 3!) - 3) \\ 69334 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F((9 + 3!))) \times 3!) - F(F(4))) \\ 69336 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + F((9 + 3!))) \times -((3 - 6)))! \\ 69342 &:= ((-((F(6))! + F(9))) + F((F(F(3)) + (4!)))) \times 2) \\ 69347 &:= (-6) + (((-9!)/F(F(3!))) \times (-4)) + F(F(7))) \\ 69348 &:= (6 \times ((F(9) \times 3!) \times F(4)) + F(F(8))) \\ 69352 &:= -(F(6) - (((F(9))^{F(3)}) \times 5!)/2)) \\ 69354 &:= (-6) - (-(((F(9))^{F(3)}) \times 5!)/F(F(4))) \\ 69360 &:= ((F(6) \times F(9)) \times ((F(3))^{F(6)}) - 0!) \\ 69363 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((F(9 \times F(3))) + (6!)) - F(F(3))) \\ 69368 &:= ((6! + F(9)) \times (F(3) - (6!/(-8)))) \\ 69373 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times (9 + F(F(3)))) + F(F(7))) - (F(3)!))! \\ 69374 &:= -(F((6 + 9)) - ((3!)^7/4)) \\ 69378 &:= (6 \times ((F(9 + 3!)) + 7) + F(F(8))) \\ 69382 &:= (((6! + F((9 \times F(3)))) \times F(8)) - 2) \\ 69383 &:= (((6! + F((9 \times F(3)))) \times F(8)) - F(F(3))) \\ 69384 &:= ((-(((6!/9)^{F(3)})) - F(F(8))) \times (-4)) \\ 69386 &:= (-F((6 + 9)) - ((3!! + F(F(8))) \times (-6))) \\ 69423 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) + (F((F(4))!)!)/2) + 3!) \\ 69426 &:= (((6! + F((9 \times F(F(4)))))) + 2) \times F(F(6)) \\ 69427 &:= (-((F(F(F(6))) + F(9))) - (((F((F(4))!)! \times (-2)) + F(F(7)))) \\ 69431 &:= (((-6!) + (9 \times F(4!)))/3!) - 1) \\ 69432 &:= (((6!/9) - F(4!)) \times (-3))/2) \\ 69433 &:= ((-6!) - ((-9) \times F(4!)) - 3!)/3! \\ 69434 &:= (((-6!) + (9 \times F(4!)))/3!) + F(F(4)) \\ 69436 &:= (((F(6))!/9) - ((F(4))!)! + (3! \times F(F(F(6)))) \\ 69438 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) + (F((F(4))!)!)/F(3)) + (F(8))) \\ 69444 &:= (((F(6) \times 9) - F(4!)) \times (-F(4)))/F(F(4)) \\ 69445 &:= (-((F(F(F(6))) + 9)) + (F(F(4)) \times ((F((F(4))!)! - 5!))) \\ 69453 &:= (-6!) - (9 \times (-(((F(4))!^5) - F(F(3!)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$69454 := -((F(F(F(6))) + (((F((9 - F(4))))! - 5!) \times (-F(F(4))))))$$

$$69464 := (-((F(F(6)) + (-F(9)) \times (F(F(4))^{F(6)}))) \times F((F(4))!))$$

$$69474 := (((F(6))! + 9) + (-4!) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))$$

$$69493 := (-F(6) - (((-F(9)) + F(4!)) \times (-9))/3!)$$

$$69524 := (-((F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) \times (-5)))) - (-2) \times (F((F(4))!))!))$$

$$69534 := ((F((6 + 9)) \times (5! - 3!)) - (F(4))!)$$

$$69535 := ((F((6 + 9)) \times (5! - 3!)) - (5))$$

$$69540 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 0$$

$$69541 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 1$$

$$69542 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 2$$

$$69543 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 3$$

$$69544 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 4$$

$$69545 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 5$$

$$69546 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 6$$

$$69547 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 7$$

$$69548 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 8$$

$$69549 := F(6 + 9) \times (5! - F(4)!) + 9$$

$$69552 := ((6 \times F(((9 - 5)!)))/(5 - F(2)))$$

$$69553 := ((6 - (-9) \times F((5!/5)))/3!)$$

$$69557 := (((F(6))! - 9!)/(-5) + (5 + 7!))$$

$$69564 := ((F((6 + 9)) \times (5! - (6))) + 4!)$$

$$69573 := (F(F(6)) \times ((9 + F((5 + F(7)))) + 3!))$$

$$69574 := (-((F(F(F(6))) - (9! - 5!))) + (-7) \times (F((F(4))!))!))$$

$$69578 := (((6! + 9!)/(-5) - (-F(7)) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$69583 := (((F(6))! + (9 - 5!)) - F(F(8))) + (F(3))!)$$

$$69587 := ((F(6))! + (F((F(9) - (5!/8))) \times 7))$$

$$69607 := ((6! \times (96 + 0!)) - F(F(7)))$$

$$69622 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (((F(9) - (F(6))!) + 2) \times (-2))))$$

$$69623 := -((F(F(F(6))) + (((-F(9)) + (F(6))!) \times (-2) + 3)))$$

$$69624 := (-F(6) - (-((F(9) \times F(6))) \times (2^{F(F(4)!)}))$$

$$69634 := -(((F(F(F(6))) + ((-F(9)) + (F(6))!) \times (-F(3)))) - F((F(4))!))$$

$$69642 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (((-F(9)) + (F(6))!) + F((F(4))!)) \times 2))$$

$$69643 := (-((F(F(F(6))) + 9)) + ((F(F(6)) - (F((F(4))!))!) \times (-F(3))))$$

$$69644 := -(((F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) - ((-(F(6))!) + F((F(4))!)) \times (-F(F(4))))))$$

$$69646 := ((F(-((6 - 9))) \times ((F(6))! - (4!))) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$69647 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (-F(9)) + (((F(6))! \times F(F(4))) - F(7))))$$

$$69648 := (6 \times (-((F(9) - 6!) + 4!)) + F(F(8)))$$

$$69657 := ((-(69) + 6!) \times (5! - F(7)))$$

$$69660 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 0$$

$$69661 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 1$$

$$69662 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 2$$

$$69663 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 3$$

$$69664 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 4$$

$$69665 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 5$$

$$69666 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 6$$

$$69667 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 7$$

$$69668 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 8$$

$$69669 := F(6)! - F(9) + F(6)! - F(F(F(6))) + 9$$

$$69673 := (((((F(6))! - F(9)) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(7)) + (F(3))!)$$

$$69674 := ((F(F(F(6))) + (-9!)/F(F(6))) \times (-7 + 4))$$

$$69676 := (((((F(6))! - 9) \times F((F(F(6))/7))) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$69678 := ((6! - 9) \times (-6 - (F(7) \times (-8))))$$

$$69682 := ((-((F(F(6)) - 9)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (8! \times (-2)))$$

$$69683 := (((((F(6))! - 9) + (F(6))!) - F(F(8))) - F(3))$$

$$69684 := (((((F(6))! - F(9)) + (F(6))!) - F(F(8))) + (4!))$$

$$69685 := (((((F(6))! - 9) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(((8 - 5))!))!)$$

$$69686 := (((((F(6))! - F((9 - 6))!) - F(F(8))) + (F(6))!)$$

$$69687 := (((((F(6))! \times F((9 - 6))) - F(F(8))) - 7)$$

$$69688 := ((-6) + (F((9 - 6)) \times 8!)) - F(F(8))$$

$$69694 := (((((F(6))! \times (-F(9))) - F(F(F(6)))) - (9! \times (-4)))$$

$$69703 := (((((F(6))! + 9) - F(F((7 + 0!)))) + (F(3))!)$$

$$69704 := (((6! \times (-9)) - F(F((7 + 0!)))) \times (-4))$$

$$69712 := -((F(F(F(6))) - ((-9) - ((7 + 1))!) \times (-2)))$$

$$69713 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F((9 + 7)))) \times (1 + 3!))$$

$$69726 := (((((F(6))! + (9 + 7)) \times 2) - F(F(F(6))))$$

$$69728 := (((((F(6))! + F(9)) + ((7 + F(2))!)) - F(F(8)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69734 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (9 \times (-F(F(7))) + F((F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(4))))))) \\
 69735 &:= ((6! \times 97) - (F(F(3!)) \times 5)) \\
 69736 &:= (((F(6))! + (F(9) - F(7))) \times F(3)) - F(F(F(6))) \\
 69738 &:= (((F(6))! + (9 + F(7))) \times F(3)) - F(F(8)) \\
 69742 &:= (-F(F(F(6)))) - (((-9) + F(7))! + (F((F(4))!))! \times (-2)) \\
 69744 &:= ((6! \times 97) + (4! \times (-4))) \\
 69746 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((-9!) - (-7!) \times F(F(4)))) / (-6)) \\
 69748 &:= (((F(6))! + (F(9) - (7))) \times F(F(4))) - F(F(8)) \\
 69752 &:= -((F(-((F(F(6)) - F(9)))) + ((7! - F(5^2)))))) \\
 69762 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) + ((F(9) + (7! \times F(6))) \times (-2))) \\
 69764 &:= (F(F(6)) + (97 \times (6! - F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 69766 &:= (((F(6))! - ((-9) - 7!) \times F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 69768 &:= (((F(F(6)))! \times (-9)) / (-7!) \times ((-6) + F(8)))! \\
 69772 &:= -((6! - ((F(9) + (7! \times (-7))) \times (-2))) \\
 69775 &:= ((6! \times 97) - (F(7) \times 5)) \\
 69776 &:= (((F(6) \times F(9)) + 7!) \times F(7)) + 6! \\
 69784 &:= ((6! \times 97) - (8! / ((F(4))!))! \\
 69786 &:= ((-6) \times (9 - 7!)) + (8! - 6!) \\
 69795 &:= ((6! \times 97) - (9 \times 5)) \\
 69798 &:= (((6! \times 97) - F(9)) - 8) \\
 69827 &:= ((6! \times (98 - F(2))) - F(7)) \\
 69834 &:= ((6! \times (F(9) - (F(8) \times (-3)))) - (F(4))! \\
 69835 &:= ((6! \times (F(9) - (F(8) \times (-3)))) - (5)) \\
 69837 &:= (((6! \times F(9)) + 8!) - 3) + 7! \\
 69838 &:= (((F(6) \times 9) + 8!) \times F(3)) - F(F(8)) \\
 69839 &:= (((F(6) - 9!) / (-8)) - (3! \times (-F(9)))) \\
 \\
 69840 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 0 \\
 69841 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 1 \\
 69842 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 2 \\
 69843 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 3 \\
 69844 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 4 \\
 69845 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 5 \\
 69846 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 6 \\
 69847 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69848 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 8 \\
 69849 &:= 6! \times (F(9) + F(8) \times F(4)) + 9 \\
 69864 &:= (((6! \times 98) - 6!) + 4!) \\
 69874 &:= -(((6! - F(9)) - ((8! \times (-7))/(-4)))) \\
 69875 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((9^{-8+F(7)} - 5!)) \\
 69883 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times 9) - F(F(8))) + ((8! \times F(3)))) \\
 69927 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) - (((9!/(-9)) \times (-2)) + F(F(7)))))) \\
 69953 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (-((F(9) - (9^5))) - F(3!))) \\
 69954 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) + (F(9) \times (-5! - ((F(4)!)!))) \\
 69963 &:= (((6! + 9) \times 96) - F(F(3!))) \\
 69964 &:= -((F(6) + (F(9) \times ((F(9) - 6!) \times F(4)))))) \\
 69966 &:= -((6! - (-99) \times (6 - 6!))) \\
 69973 &:= ((-6) + F((F(9) - 9))) - ((7! + 3!)) \\
 69974 &:= ((-F(6) + F((F(9) - 9))) - ((7! + F(4)))) \\
 69977 &:= -(((F(6) - F((9 + 9) + 7)) + 7!)) \\
 69978 &:= (6! + ((F(9) \times 97) \times F(8))) \\
 69986 &:= (((6! \times (9 \times 9)) + F(F(8))) + (6!)) \\
 69987 &:= ((-6) + F((F(9) - 9))) - (-8 + 7!) \\
 69993 &:= ((F(6) + F((F(9) - 9))) - ((9 - F(3)))!) \\
 69996 &:= ((6! + F(F((9 - (9/9)))))) \times 6 \\
 69996 &:= ((6! + F(F((9 - (9/9)))))) \times 6 \\
 69997 &:= ((F(F(6)) + F((F(9) - 9))) - (9 + 7!)) \\
 70234 &:= (((F(7) - 0!) \times F((-F(2)) + F(F(3)))) - F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) \\
 70266 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times (((F(2) + (6)))! - F(F(6)))) \\
 70273 &:= (7 \times (0! + (2 \times (7! - F(F(3)))))) \\
 70327 &:= ((7! \times ((0! + 3!) \times 2)) - F(F(7))) \\
 70336 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-0!) + F(F(3!))) + (3! \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 70338 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 0!) \times (F(3)^{F(3!)})) + F(F(8))) \\
 70343 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - ((0! + 3!)!) - (4^{F(3!)})) \\
 70378 &:= ((7! - F((0! + 3!))) \times (-7 + F(8))) \\
 70395 &:= ((F((7 + 0!)) + 3!) \times 95) \\
 70434 &:= ((-((7! - 0!)) + F((F(4)!)!)) \times (-F(3!) + (F(4)!)!)) \\
 70447 &:= ((-F((F(7) + 0!))) + (F(4!)/F((F(4)!)!)) \times F(7)) \\
 70448 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times (((F(4) + (4)))! - 8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 70473 &:= (((-(F(7) + 0!)) \times ((F(4))! - (7!))) - 3) \\
 70474 &:= (((-(F(7) + 0!)) \times ((F(4))! - (7!))) - F(F(4))) \\
 70476 &:= ((F(7) + ((0 \times 4)!) \times (7! - (6))) \\
 70483 &:= (((-F(F(7))) + ((0! + (F(4))!))!) + (F(F(8)) \times 3!)) \\
 70492 &:= (((-(7!) \times (-0! - (F(4))!)) - F(9)) \times 2) \\
 70494 &:= (((-(7! - 0!)) + (F((F(4))!))!) - F(9)) \times F(F(4)) \\
 70497 &:= (((7! \times (0! - F(4))) + 9) \times (-7)) \\
 70532 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times (((5 + F(3)))! - 2)) \\
 70536 &:= (((7! + 0!) - (5)) \times 3!) + (F(6))! \\
 70544 &:= (((-(7!) + (F((0! + (5))))!) - F((F(4))!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 70547 &:= -((F(7) + ((0! + (-5) \times F(4))) \times 7!)) \\
 70548 &:= (((-(7!) + F(F(-(0! - (5)))))) \times (-F(4))!) + 8! \\
 \\
 70560 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 0 \\
 70561 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 1 \\
 70562 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 2 \\
 70563 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 3 \\
 70564 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 4 \\
 70565 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 5 \\
 70566 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 6 \\
 70567 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 7 \\
 70568 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 8 \\
 70569 &:= 7! \times (0! + 5 + F(6)) + 9 \\
 \\
 70573 &:= ((F(7) + (F((0! + (5))))!) + (7! \times 3!)) \\
 70574 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times ((5 + 7!) - (4))) \\
 70576 &:= 7! + (0! - 5)^{-F(7)+F(F(6))} \\
 70594 &:= (((7! \times (0! + (5))) + F(9)) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 70599 &:= (-F(F(7))) \times (F(-(0! - (5)))) - (9 \times F(9))) \\
 70637 &:= ((7! - 0!) + (6 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - F(7)))) \\
 70638 &:= (((F(7) + ((0! + (6)))!) \times 3!) + 8!) \\
 70644 &:= (7 \times (((0! + (6)))! + (F(4))!) \times F(F(4))) \\
 70664 &:= ((F(F((7 + 0!))) - ((F(6))! / (-6))) \times 4) \\
 70665 &:= (-7!) + (((0! + 6!) \times F(F(6))) \times 5) \\
 70668 &:= (7! + (06 \times (-F(6) + F(F(8))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}70671 &:= (((F(7) + 0!) \times (F(6) + 7!)) - 1) \\70672 &:= ((7! + F(06)) \times (7 \times 2)) \\70673 &:= (((F(7) + 0!) \times (F(6) + 7!)) + F(F(3))) \\70674 &:= (((F(7) + 0!) \times (F(6) + 7!)) + F(F(4))) \\70677 &:= (((7! + 0!) + F(6)) \times F(7)) + 7! \\70685 &:= ((7! - 0!) + (6 \times (F(F(8)) - (5)))) \\70686 &:= (((7! + 0!) + F(6)) \times (8 + 6)) \\70716 &:= (7! + (F(F((07 + 1))) \times 6)) \\70728 &:= (7! + (-((0! - (7))) \times (2 + F(F(8)))))) \\70734 &:= (7! - ((F(F((0! + (7)))) + 3) \times (-F(4)!))) \\70742 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times (F(7) + (((F(4))! + F(2))))!) \\70749 &:= (((F(7) + 0!) \times 7!) + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times 9)) \\70764 &:= (7! - (((0! + (7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(4)!))) \\70784 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times ((7! - 8) + 4!)) \\70786 &:= ((70 + 7!) + (F(F(8)) \times 6)) \\70793 &:= (F(F(7)) - (-((0! + F(7))) \times ((9 - F(3))!)) \\70798 &:= ((F(7) + 0!) \times (7! + ((9 + 8)))) \\70824 &:= (((-7) + F((0! + F(8)))) + 2) \times 4 \\ \\70830 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 0 \\70831 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 1 \\70832 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 2 \\70833 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 3 \\70834 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 4 \\70835 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 5 \\70836 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 6 \\70837 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 7 \\70838 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 8 \\70839 &:= (7! + F(-0! + F(8))) \times 3! + 9 \\ \\70842 &:= (((-((7 \times 0))!) - F(F(8))) + F(4!)) \times 2 \\70843 &:= ((F(((7 \times 0))! + F(8))) \times 4) - F(F(3)) \\70844 &:= ((F(((7 \times 0))! + F(8))) \times F(F(4))) \times F(F(4)) \\70848 &:= ((F((F(7) + 0!)) - 8) \times (4! \times 8)) \\70851 &:= (7 - (F((0! + F(8))) \times (-5 - 1)))\end{aligned}$$

- 70854 := ((F(7) + 0!) × (F(8) + ((5 + F(F(4))))!))
70863 := (F(7) × (-(0! + F(8))) - (F(F(F(6)))/(-F(3))))
70864 := (((-F(7)) - F((0! + F(8)))) + F(6)) × (-4)
70866 := (((7! + F(-(0! - F(8)))) + 6) × 6)
70868 := (((7! + 0!) + F(8)) × (6 + 8))
70871 := (((F(7) - 0!) × (F(F(8)) - (7!))) - 1)
70872 := ((7! - F(F(08))) × (-F(7) - F(2)))
70873 := (((F(7) - 0!) × (F(F(8)) - (7!))) + F(F(3)))
70874 := (((F(7) - 0!) × (F(F(8)) - (7!))) + F(F(4)))
70884 := (((7! - 0!) - F(F(8))) × (-(8 + 4)))
70991 := (((F(F(7)) - 0!) × (9 × F(9))) - 1)
70992 := ((F(F(7)) - 0!) × ((9 × F(9)) × F(2)))
70993 := (((F(F(7)) - 0!) × (9 × F(9))) + F(F(3)))
70994 := (((F(F(7)) - 0!) × (9 × F(9))) + F(F(4)))
71046 := (7! + ((F(10) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) × 6))
71064 := ((71 + 0!) × F(-(F(6) - 4!)))
71077 := (F(((F(7) + (7)) - 0!)) × 17)
71136 := ((7 + F(11)) × (3!! + F(F(6))))
71274 := (((7⁽¹⁺²⁾)! - (7)) - F(4!))
71344 := (((F(7) + 1)³) × (F(F(4)) + (4!)))
71395 := (((-((7! + 1)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 9!)/(-5))
71426 := (F(F((7 + 1))) + (((F(4)²)!)/6))
71433 := (7 - (((1 + F((F(4))!))!)/(-3!)) - F(F(F(3!))))
71435 := ((7! - 1) + ((F(4))! × (F(F(F(3!))) + 5!)))
71436 := ((F(F((7 + 1))) × (F(4))!) - (F(3!) × (-6!)))
71438 := (((7! + 1) × (4 × 3)) + F(F(8)))
71443 := (((-((7! - 1)) + (4^{F(F(4))})) + F(F(F(3!))))
71454 := (((7 - 1) × F((4! - (5)))) + F(4!))
71466 := ((F(F(7)) - (((1 × 4)!)/F(F(6))!)) × (-6))
71474 := (((F(7) - 1) × (4 + 7!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
71475 := ((F(F(7)) + ((F((1 × 4))!))! × 75)
71484 := (7 × ((-14) + F(F(8))) - ((F(4))!))
71544 := (((7! × (1 × 5)) + F(4!)) - (4!))
71547 := (((F(F((7 + 1))) - (5)) - ((F(4))!))! × 7)

- 71547 := $(-(7) \times (((F(4))!)! - (-5) + F(F((1 + 7))))))$
- 71563 := $((7! - 1) \times 5) + F((F(6) \times 3))$
- 71567 := $(-(7! + 15)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7))$
- 71573 := $((7! + 1) \times 5) + F(((7 - 3))!)$
- 71574 := $((7 - 1) - (-5) \times 7!) + F(4!)$
- 71575 := $((7 + F(-((1 - 5)))!) + (7! \times 5))$
- 71576 := $((7 \times F(F(F((1 + 5)))))) - ((7! + (6))))$
- 71578 := $(-(7! - ((1 - 5)))) - (-7) \times F(F(8)))$
- 71581 := $((7 \times (-((1 + 5))!) + F(F(8)))) - 1$
- 71582 := $(7 \times (-((1 + 5))!) + F((F(8) \times F(2))))$
- 71583 := $((7 \times (-((1 + 5))!) + F(F(8))) + F(F(3)))$
- 71584 := $((7! - 1) \times 5) + F(8) + F(4!)$
- 71587 := $((7! \times (-1)) + 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))$
- 71637 := $(-(7! + 1) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F(3!)) \times 7))$
- 71637 := $((7 \times (F(3!) + F(F(F(6)))))) - (1 + 7!)$
- 71638 := $(7 \times ((F((1 \times 6)) - 3!) + F(F(8))))$
- 71673 := $(7 \times (F(F(F((1 \times 6)))))) - (-F(7) + 3!))$
- 71678 := $((F(7) - 1) \times (F(F(6)) + (7!))) + F(F(8))$
- 71736 := $(7 \times (((1 - F(F(7))) + 3!) \times F(F(6))))$
- 71737 := $(-(7! + 1) + ((7! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-F(7))))$
- 71737 := $((7! - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-F(7)) - (1 + 7!))$
- 71738 := $((F(7) + 1) \times (-7! + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(F(8)))$
- 71743 := $((F(F(7)) \times (-1 + (F(7) \times 4!))) - 3!)$
- 71856 := $((-((F(7) - 1) - F(8)))! / 5) - (6!)$
- 71877 := $((F((F(7) + 1)) - F(F(8))) + (7!)) \times (-F(7))$
- 71877 := $(F(7) \times ((-7!) + F(F(8))) - F((1 + F(7))))$
- 71894 := $(((-7) - F((-1 + F(8)))) \times (-9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))$
- 71936 := $(7! + ((F(19) \times F(3)) \times F(6)))$
- 71967 := $(-7! - ((F(F(F(6))) + F((9 + 1))) \times (-7)))$
- 71967 := $(-7! + ((F((1 + 9)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7))$
- 72035 := $((7 - (-20) \times 3!)) \times 5$
- 72065 := $((F(7) - (-20) \times 6!)) \times 5$
- 72072 := $((-((F(7))!) / (((2 + 0))!)!) / (-((7 - 2))!))$
- 72145 := $(F(((F(7) \times 2) - 1)) - (4! \times 5!))$
- 72177 := $((F(F(7)) - (2 \times (1 - 7!))) \times 7)$

- 72303 := ((7! - F((2 × F(3!)) + 0!)) × F(F(3!)))
 72324 := ((-7!) - F((2 × F(3!)))) × (-2) × (F(4)!)
 72338 := (7 × ((-2) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(-(3! - F(8))))
 72343 := (-F(F(7))) - (((F(2) + F(3!))!)/(-F(4) + F(3)))
 72345 := -(((F(F(7)) - 2) - ((3 × F(4))!/5))
 72352 := ((F((F(7) + 2)) - F(3)) × (5! - F(2)))
 72357 := -(((F((F(7) + 2)) × (F(F(3)) - 5!)) + F(F(7))))
 72366 := (7 × ((2 - F((-3!) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6))))
 72373 := (-((7²)) × (3!! - (F(7)³)))
 72374 := (F(7) + (((2^{F(3!)}) + F(7))^{F(F(4))}))
 72384 := ((F((7 × 2)) × 3!) × (8 × 4))
 72386 := (((-7!) × (2^{F(3!)}))/(-F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))
 72432 := (((7 + 2)! - ((F(4))!)/3) + 2)
 72433 := ((F(F(7))²) + ((-F(4!)) + (F(3!))!) × (-3))
 72434 := ((-7) + F((F(2) + 4!))) - F((3! × F(4)))
 72438 := ((F(F((7 + F(2)))) × F(4)) - (3!! - 8!))
 72441 := (-F((72/4))) + F((4! + 1))
 72445 := (F(7) - (((F(2) + F((F(4))!))! - ((F(4))!)/(-5)))
 72448 := ((7 + F((F(2) + 4!))) - F(-(F(4) - F(8))))
 72452 := ((F((F(7) + 2)) + 4) × (5! - 2))
 72453 := (((7 + 2)! - ((F(4))!)/5) + F(F(3!)))
 72454 := ((F(7) + F((-2) + 4!)) + (5 × F(F(F((F(4))!))))
 72458 := ((F(F(7)) × (F((2 × (F(4))!) + 5!)) + F(F(8)))
 72459 := ((F(7) - ((2 × 4)!/5)) × (-9))
 72463 := (F(F(7)) × (-F(2)) + (4! × (F(F(6)) - F(3!))))
 72464 := ((F(F(7)) × ((F(2) + 4)!) - F(6)) + F(4!))
 72474 := (((F((F(7) - F(2))) - (F(4))!) × F(F(7))) + (F((F(4))!))!)
 72484 := (((7!/(-2)) - F(F((F(4))!))) + (F((F(8) + 4))))
 72488 := (F(7) × (((-2) + ((F(4))!)) - (F(8))) × 8))
 72495 := -(((7 + 2)^{F(F(4))}) + (9!/(-5)))
 72499 := (((7!/(-2)) - (F(4))!) + F((F(9) - 9)))
 72505 := ((7!/(-2)) + F((5 × 05)))
 72526 := (((7!/(-2)) + F(5²)) + F(F(6)))
 72534 := (((7 + 2)!/5) - (F(F(3!)) × F(F(4))))

$$\begin{aligned}72537 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - (3 \times F(7))) \\72539 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - 3) - F(9) \\72542 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F((F(4)^2))) \\72544 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - 4!) - F((F(4))!) \\72546 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - 4!) - (6) \\72549 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - (F(4) \times 9)) \\72552 &:= (((((7 + 2))! - 5!)/5) \times F(2)) \\72553 &:= (((((7 + 2))! - 5!)/5) + F(F(3))) \\72554 &:= (((((7 + 2))! - 5!)/5) + F(F(4))) \\72556 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - (5!/6)) \\72563 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F(F(6))) + F(3!) \\72564 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F(6)) - (4) \\72567 &:= ((F((7 + F(2))) - 5!) \times -(6! + F(7))) \\72573 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F((7 - 3))) \\72574 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F((7 - 4))) \\72575 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F((7 - 5))) \\72579 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + F((F(7) - 9))) \\72582 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + (8 - 2)) \\72583 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + (F(8)/3)) \\72584 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + F((F((8 - 4))!)) \\72589 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) - F(8)) + F(9) \\72590 &:= (F((F(7) + 2)) \times (5! - ((9 \times 0)!)) \\72593 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + (F(9)/F(3))) \\72594 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + (9 \times F(F(4)))) \\72597 &:= (((((7 + 2))!)/5) + F(9)) - F(7) \\72624 &:= (-((7^{-2+6})) + F((F(2) + 4!))) \\72625 &:= ((7^2) + (((F(6) + F(2))!)/5)) \\72632 &:= (((7 \times (2 + F(F(F(6)))))) - (F(3!)!) \times 2) \\72644 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \times 4!) - 4) \\72648 &:= ((F(7) - F(2)) \times ((6 + F(4!)) - 8!)) \\72650 &:= ((F(7) + (2 \times 6!)) \times 50) \\72665 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F(2) + F(6))! - (6!))/5)) \\72666 &:= (((F(7) \times F((2 \times F(6)))) - (6!)) \times 6) \\72668 &:= (-F(7)) - ((F((-2) + F(F(6)))) - (6!)) \times (-F(8))) \\72674 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F((-2) + F(F(6)))) + (7 \times F(F(F((F(4))!))))\end{aligned}$$

- 72683** := $(F(7) \times (-F(2) - ((6! - F(8)) \times F(3))))$
72690 := $(7! + (F((-F(2) + F(F(6)))) \times (9 + 0!)))$
72722 := $(F(7) \times (2 - (F(F(7)) \times (-((2 + 2)!))))$
72743 := $((F(7) \times (2 - (F(F(7)) \times (-4!))) + F(F(3!)))$
72744 := $((F(F(7)) \times (F(2) \times F(7))) + F(F(4))) \times 4!$
72745 := $((F(7)^2) + (((F(7) - (4))!)/5))$
72747 := $((7! \times (2 \times 7)) + (F(4)^7))$
72765 := $((F(F(7)) - 2) \times 7!) / (F(F(6)) - (5))$
72774 := $(F(7) \times (-((F(2) - (7))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-4!))))$
72795 := $(F(F(7)) + (-((2 \times 7) - (9!/(-5))))$
72837 := $(F(F(7)) + (2 \times (-8!) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-7))))$
72847 := $((7!/(-2)) \times (-F(8) - F((F(4)!))) - F(F(7)))$
72848 := $((7!/2) - 8) \times (F((F(4)!)) + (F(8)))$
72853 := $(-((F(F(7)) + ((2 - (8^5)))))) + (F(3)!)$
72854 := $(-((F(F(7)) + ((F(2) - (8^5)))))) + (F((F(4)!))!)$
72856 := $(-(((F(F(7)) - (F(2) + (8^5))) - (F(6)!)))$
72864 := $(((((F(7) - F(2)) - 8)!)/F(F(6)!)) \times (F(4)!)$
72866 := $(F(F((7 + F(2)))) - (-86) \times 6!)$
72868 := $((F(F(7))^2 - 8!) \times 6 - F(F(8)))$
72933 := $((-((F(7)^2)) - (-F(9) \times 3!)) \times 3)$
72934 := $((F(F(7)) \times (2^9)) + 3!) - F(4!)$
72947 := $((-((F(7) + (2^9))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 7)$
72952 := $(F((7 \times 2)) + ((9!/5) - F(2)))$
72953 := $((F((7 \times 2)) - (9!/(-5))) \times F(F(3)))$
72954 := $((F((7 \times 2)) - (9!/(-5))) + F(F(F(4))))$
72965 := $(-((F(F(7)) - (-2) + (F((9 + 6)) \times 5!))))$
72967 := $((((7 - 2)! \times F((9 + 6))) - F(F(7)))$
72984 := $((F(7) - F(2)) \times ((F(9) - 8!) + F(4!)))$
73038 := $((73 + 0!) \times F((F(3) \times 8)))$
73054 := $((F(F(7)) \times 3 + 0!) \times 5! - F(F(F((F(4)!))))$
73075 := $((-F(7) + (F(3)!)) + (((0! + (7))^5)))$
73094 := $(7 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F(-((0! - 9))) \times 4!)))$
73095 := $((7 + (F(3)!)) + (-((0! - 9))^5))$
73134 := $((((-7) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 1) \times 3) + (F((F(4)!))!)$
73144 := $(((-F(7) + (F(3)!)) - 1) + (F(4) \times F(F(F((F(4)!))))))$

- 73146 := (((-(F(7)) + (F(3!)!) + 1) + (F(4) × F(F(F(6))))))
- 73148 := (-(F(7)) - (((F(F(F(3!))) + 1) × (-F(4))) - 8!))
- 73158 := ((F((7 × 3)) × F(-(1 - 5))) + 8!)
- 73164 := (((7 + (F(3!)!) - 1) + (F(F(F(6))) × F(4)))
- 73165 := ((F(F(7)) + (3!! × (-1 + F(F(6)))) × 5)
- 73168 := (7 + ((3 × (1 + F(F(F(6)))) + 8!))
- 73173 := ((F(F(7)) × (-3) + F((-1 + F(7)))) + (F(3!)!)
- 73187 := (-(F(7)) + (((3! - 1)! × F((8 + 7))))
- 73193 := (-7) + (((3! - 1)! × F((9 + 3!))))
- 73200 := (F((F(7) + F(3))) × (((2 + 0!)! - 0!)!)
- 73234 := (7 × (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(2) + F(F(3!)))^{F(F(4))})))
- 73236 := (((F(7) × F(3!)) - 2) × (-F(3) - 6!))
- 73249 := (F(7) + ((3!! - 2) × (F(4) × F(9))))
- 73274 := (((-(F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) × 2) + (7! + F(4!)))
- 73275 := ((F(F(7)) × 3) + (((2 + 7)!/5))
- 73276 := (7 × (F(F(F(3!))) - (2 × (F(F(7)) + 6))))
- 73294 := (((F(7) × ((3 × 2)!) × 9) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))
- 73295 := (((F((7 - 3)))!)! - ((F(2) + (9!/(-5))))
- 73309 := -((F(F(7)) - (3 × ((3!! + 0!) × F(9))))
- 73318 := ((7 × F(F(F(3!)))) - (3!! + F(18)))
- 73324 := (((7!/(-3)) - F(F(3!))) + (F((F(2) + 4!))))
- 73333 := (F(7) × ((F(F(F(3!)))/F(3)) + (F(3!) × F(F(3!))))
- 73334 := (((F(7) + F(F(F(3!))))/(-3)) + (F(3!)!) × F(F(4)))
- 73336 := (((F(7) × F(3!)) + 3!!) × F((3 + F(6))))
- 73337 := (((7 - 3!) × 3!!) + F(F(3)))/(-7)
- 73337 := (((7 - 3!) × 3!!) + F(F(3)))/(-7)
- 73341 := ((F((7 + F(F(3!)))) × 3)/F(((F(4)! + 1)))
- 73342 := (((7!/(-3)) - 3) + F((4! + F(2))))
- 73343 := (((7!/(-3)) - F(3)) + F((4! + F(F(3))))
- 73344 := (((F(7) × 3!!) - (F(3!) × 4!)) × F((F(4)!))
- 73345 := ((7!/(-3)) + F(((F(3) + F(4)) × 5)))
- 73346 := (((7! - 3)/(-3)) + F((4 + F(F(6))))
- 73348 := (((7!/(-3)) + 3) + F((4 + F(8))))
- 73352 := -((((F(F(7)) + 3!!) + 3!!) - F((5²))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 73353 &:= (((7!/(-3)) + F(3!)) + F(5^{F(3)})) \\
 73358 &:= (F(F(7)) - ((3^{F(3!)} \times (-5)) - 8!)) \\
 73359 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(F(F(3!)))/F(3)) - (-5 \times F(9)))) \\
 73360 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(3))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (F(6) - 0!)) \\
 73362 &:= (7! + (3! \times (F(F(F(3!))) + ((F(F(6))^2)))) \\
 73365 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!))) \times 3) - 6) \times 5 \\
 73368 &:= (7! + (((F(F(3!))^3) - (6!)) \times 8)) \\
 73374 &:= (((7!/F(3!))/F(3)) \times F(F(7))) - F(F((F(4)!))) \\
 73378 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(7) - 8!))) \\
 73383 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F(3!))!) + ((3 \times F(F(8))) - F(3!))) \\
 73388 &:= ((F(F(7)) - 3) - ((-3) \times F(F(8))) - 8!) \\
 73389 &:= ((-(7! - 3)) + 3!!) \times (-8 + 9)) \\
 73391 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F(3!))!) + (3 \times F(F((9 - 1)))) \\
 73393 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!))) \times (3! + 9)) - F(3)) \\
 73394 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(3) + (F(3)^9))) - F(4!)) \\
 73395 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (-3) \times ((3! + 9) - 5!)) \\
 73398 &:= ((F(7) \times (F(3!) + (3!! \times 9))) - F(F(8))) \\
 73399 &:= (-7) + ((3!! \times (3 \times F(9))) - F(9)) \\
 73416 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(3!)) - (F(4)!)) + 1) \times F(F(6))) \\
 73419 &:= (F(7) + (((3!! \times F(4)) - 1) \times F(9))) \\
 73427 &:= (-F(7)) - (3!! \times (-F(4) \times F((2 + 7)))) \\
 73428 &:= (((F((F(7) + 3!)) - F(4!)) \times (-2)) - F(F(8))) \\
 73433 &:= (-7) - (3!! \times (-F(4) \times F((3 \times 3)))) \\
 73434 &:= (((F(7) \times 3!) + 4!) \times 3!!) - (F(4)!)) \\
 73435 &:= (((F(7) \times 3!) + 4!) \times 3!!) - (5) \\
 73437 &:= ((F(7) \times F(F(3!))) \times ((F(F(4))^{F(3!)} + F(7))) \\
 73437 &:= ((F(7) \times F(F(3!))) \times ((F(F(4))^{F(3!)} + F(7))) \\
 73439 &:= ((-7) + 3!) - ((F(4) \times 3!!) \times (-F(9))) \\
 \\
 73440 &:= (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 0 \\
 73441 &:= (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 1 \\
 73442 &:= (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 2 \\
 73443 &:= (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 3 \\
 73444 &:= (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 4 \\
 73445 &:= (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$73446 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 6$$

$$73447 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 7$$

$$73448 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 8$$

$$73449 := (-7! + 3!! \times 4!) \times F(4)! + 9$$

$$73453 := (F(7) - (3!! \times ((4! - 5!) - 3!)))$$

$$73454 := (((7 + (F(3!))!) - (((F(4))!) \times 5)) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$73455 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(4))!) - (5^5))$$

$$73458 := ((F(7) + (3^{F(4)!})) \times (5! - F(8)))$$

$$73463 := ((F(F(7)) + (F(3!))!) + ((4! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3))$$

$$73464 := (((F(7) \times 3!) + 4!) \times 6!) + 4!$$

$$73465 := (((7! / (-3)) + F((4 + F(F(6)))))) + 5!$$

$$73469 := (F(F(7)) - (((3! - (F(4) \times 6!)) \times F(9))))$$

$$73472 := (7 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F((F(4))!) - F(F(7))) \times (-2)))$$

$$73474 := (((-7!) + 3!!) - F(F(4))) \times (7 - 4!)$$

$$73477 := (((7! + (F(3!))!) / F((F(4))!)) \times F(7) - F(F(7)))$$

$$73478 := (((7 \times 3!)^{F(4)} - F((7 + 8)))$$

$$73486 := (7 \times (((F(3!))!) / ((F(4))!)) \times (-8) + F(F(F(6))))$$

$$73493 := (-((F(F(7)) - ((-3!) \times F(4!)) + 9!)) - F(F(F(3!))))$$

$$73494 := ((F(7) - (F(3!)^4)) \times (-9) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$73495 := -((F(F(7)) - ((3!! \times (F(F(4))^9)) / 5))$$

$$73496 := ((7 \times F(3!)) + ((F(4) \times F(9)) \times 6!))$$

$$73500 := ((-7) \times F(F(3!))) \times (-500)$$

$$73504 := ((F(7) \times (3 - 5!)) + F((0! + 4!)))$$

$$73528 := ((-F(7)) + 3!!) \times (5! - ((2 \times 8)))$$

$$73534 := -((F((7 + F(F(3!)))) + (-((5^{F(3!)})) - ((F(4))!)))$$

$$73537 := ((7 + (3!! / 5)) \times (3!! - F(F(7))))$$

$$73537 := ((7 + (3!! / 5)) \times (3!! - F(F(7))))$$

$$73542 := ((F(7) + F((3! + (5)))) \times (((F(4))!) + F(2)))$$

$$73543 := ((F(7) \times (3! - 5!)) + F((4! + F(F(3))))$$

$$73544 := ((7! \times 3!) - ((-5!) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-4))$$

$$73554 := (((F(7) + 3!!) - 5!) \times 5!) - (F(4))!$$

$$73555 := (((F(7) + 3!!) - 5!) \times 5!) - (5)$$

$$73560 := (((F(7) + 3!!) - 5!) \times ((6 - 0)!))$$

$$73563 := (((7 + F(3))!) / 5) + F((F(6) \times F(3)))$$

- 73572 := $((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (5 \times F((F(7) + 2))))$
- 73574 := $((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((5! + (7)) \times 4!))$
- 73577 := $((F((F(7) + F(3))) \times 5!) + (F((7 + 7))))$
- 73584 := $(((((F(7) \times F(3)) + 5!) \times F(8)) \times 4!))$
- 73595 := $((((-7!) - F((F(3) \times 5))) - 9!) / (-5))$
- 73626 := $((-7!) - (F(3) \times (F((F(6) \times 2)) - (F(6)!))))$
- 73627 := $((F(F(7)) \times (-3!)) + F(((6 \times 2) + F(7))))$
- 73632 := $((F(7) \times F(3!)) \times (6! - (3! \times 2)))$
- 73633 := $((F(F(7)) \times 363) - F(F(F(3!))))$
- 73639 := $(F(F(7)) - (((3 \times 6!) - F(F(3))) \times (-F(9))))$
- 73642 := $((-(F(F(7))) - F(-(F(F(3)) - F(F(6)))))) - ((F((F(4)!))!) \times (-2)))$
- 73644 := $(F((7 + F(3))) \times ((6! \times F(4)) + (F(4)!)))$
- 73645 := $((F(7) + (3!/F(6))) \times (((F(4)!))! - (5)))$
- 73647 := $((((7! \times F(3)) + (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))})) \times 7)$
- 73648 := $((((F(F(7)) \times (-3!)) + F(F(6))) + F((4 + F(8))))$
- 73649 := $(F(F(7)) + (3 \times (-F(6)) - (((F(4)!))! \times (-F(9))))))$
- 73654 := $((-(((F(7) + F(3)) - 6!) \times 5!)) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))$
- 73656 := $(((((7 - 3)! + 6!) \times (5! - F(F(6))))$
- 73664 := $((((-F(7)) + F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \times F(6)) + (F((F(4)!))!))$
- 73672 := $((-((7! + 3!)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(7)))) / (-2))$
- 73673 := $(F(F(7)) - (3! \times (-((F(6) \times F(7)) - F(3))))$
- 73678 := $((7 - (-3 \times 6!)) \times (F(7) + F(8)))$
- 73679 := $((7 \times (-3!) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-9)))$
- 73682 := $(7 \times ((F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(8)^2))))$
- 73684 := $((((-7) + (F(3)!))! - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(8))) \times 4)$
- 73694 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F(3!))) + (((6! \times F(9)) \times F(4))))$
- 73696 := $((7! + F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - 9) \times F(6)$
- 73715 := $((7! \times (-3)) + F((F(7) + 1))) \times (-5)$
- 73719 := $((((7!/F(3!)) \times (-F(7))) - 1) \times (-9))$
- 73732 := $(((((7 + F(3)))! / 7) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2)))$
- 73734 := $((((-7!) - (F(3)!))! \times (-F(7))) / F(3!)) + (4!))$
- 73735 := $((F(F(7)) - (((3! \times 7)^3) - 5!))$
- 73736 := $((F(7) \times F(3!)) \times (-((F(7) - F(3)) - 6!)))$
- 73738 := $((-((7! - 3!)) - F(F(7))) \times (-3! + 8))$

$$\begin{aligned}73741 &:= (F(7) - (-((F(3)^{F(7)})) \times (F((F(4))!) + 1))) \\73742 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((-7!) - ((F(4))!) / (-2))) \\73744 &:= ((F((F(7) + 3!)) + ((7! - F(4)))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\73745 &:= ((7^3) \times ((7!/4!) + (5))) \\73746 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(3!)) \times ((F(7) \times 4!) - (6))) \\73749 &:= (F(7) \times (((3 + F(F(7))) \times 4!) + 9)) \\73763 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F(F(7)) + (6!)) \times 3)) \\73764 &:= (((7! + F((3! + F(7)))) \times F(6)) - 4) \\73768 &:= ((7! + F((3! + (7 + 6)))) \times 8) \\73784 &:= (((7! + (F(3!))!) - F(F(7))) + F((F(8) + F(F(4))))) \\73788 &:= (F(7) \times (3! - ((7! + 8!) / (-8)))) \\73790 &:= (((7 + (F(3)^{F(7)})) \times 9) - 0!) \\73800 &:= (((F(7))! / (F(3!))!) - ((8! \times (0! + 0!))) \\73802 &:= (((F(7))! / (F(3!))!) + ((8! - 0!) \times (-2))) \\73822 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(8) - F(2))^2))) \\73824 &:= (((F(7))! / (F(3!))!) + ((8! \times (-2)) + 4!)) \\73833 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(3!)) + F(F(8))) \times 3) + (F(3!))! \\73834 &:= ((-F(F(7))) - F(F(3!))) + ((F(8) \times F(3))^{F(4)}) \\73836 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-3! - F(8))) + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(6))) \\73842 &:= (((F(7))! / (F(3!))!) + ((-8!) + F(F((F(4))!))) \times 2) \\73844 &:= ((-F(7)) + (F(F(3!)) \times F((F(8) - (4)))) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\73846 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (((F(3) \times 8!) - (F(4)^{F(6)})))) \\73848 &:= (((F(F(7)) - 3) + F(F(8))) \times F(4)) + 8! \\73855 &:= (((-F(7)) \times 3!!) / 8) + F((5 \times 5)) \\73856 &:= (((F(7) \times 3!!) - (8 + 5!)) \times F(6)) \\73859 &:= (-F(7)) - (((3!! + 8!) / 5) \times (-9)) \\73862 &:= (-((F(7) - (F(3) \times 8!))) - F((F(F(6)) - F(2)))) \\73863 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - F(3!)) - ((F(8) + F(F(6)))^3))) \\73864 &:= ((7 + (F(3!))!) + (F(8) \times F((F(F(6)) - 4)))) \\73865 &:= ((F(7) - F(3)) \times ((8! / 6) - (5))) \\73868 &:= ((-((7! \times (F(3) - F(8)))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(8))) \\73873 &:= ((F((F(7) - F(3))) \times F((F(8) - (7)))) + (F(3!))!) \\73878 &:= ((F((F(7) + 3)) \times (F(8) + F(7))) + 8!) \\73882 &:= ((7 + (F(3) \times 8!)) - F((F(8) - F(2))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 73883 &:= -(((F(F(7)) \times (F(3!) + (F(8)))) - ((8! \times F(3)))))) \\
 73888 &:= ((F(7) - F(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) + ((8! + 8!))) \\
 73894 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((F(F(8)) - F(9))/4)) \\
 73912 &:= ((F(7) \times F((F(3) \times 9))) + (F(((1 + 2)!)))! \\
 73913 &:= (((F(7) \times F((F(3) \times 9))) + 1) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 73920 &:= ((7!/3!) \times (F((9 + 2)) - 0!)) \\
 73924 &:= (((-F(7)) \times (F(3!) - F(9)))^2) - (F((F(4)!))!) \\
 73926 &:= (((((7 - F(3)))! - 9)^2) \times 6) \\
 73927 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (F((9 + F(2))) \times 7))) \\
 73928 &:= ((-7) - (F(3!) \times (-F(9)^2))) \times 8 \\
 73931 &:= (F(7) \times (((3!! - 9) \times F(3!)) - 1)) \\
 73933 &:= (((F(7) \times F((F(3) \times 9))) + F(F(3!))) + (F(3!)!)) \\
 73934 &:= (((7^{F(3)}) \times (-F(9)) + 3!!) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 73936 &:= (((F(7) \times (3!! - 9)) - F(F(3))) \times F(6)) \\
 73937 &:= (-7) - (((3!! - 9) \times F(3!)) \times (-F(7))) \\
 73937 &:= (-7) - (((3!! - 9) \times F(3!)) \times (-F(7))) \\
 73938 &:= ((F(7) \times (F(3) + F((9 \times F(3)))))) + 8! \\
 73941 &:= ((-7) \times F(F(3!))) \times ((-9!)/(F(4)!)) + 1) \\
 73942 &:= (((F(7) \times (3!! - 9)) \times F((F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 73943 &:= (((F(7) \times (3!! - 9)) \times F((F(4)!)) - F(F(3))) \\
 73944 &:= (((7^3) \times 9) - (F(4)!)) \times 4! \\
 73946 &:= (((7! \times 3) + 9!)/(F(4)!)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 73953 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 3!) - (9!/(-5))) - F(F(3!))) \\
 73969 &:= (((F(7)^3) \times F(9)) - 6!) - 9 \\
 73974 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 3!) + (9!/(7 - F(F(4)))))) \\
 73975 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 9)) - F((F(7) + (5)))) \\
 73976 &:= (7 \times ((3! \times (-9 \times 7)) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 73983 &:= ((-7) + 3!) + ((F(9) \times 8)^{F(3)}) \\
 73984 &:= ((-F(7)) \times F(3!)) + ((F(9) + 8)^{F(4)}) \\
 73986 &:= (((F(7)^3) \times F(9)) + 8) - 6! \\
 73987 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(3!)) \times (F(9) + (F(8) \times F(7)))) \\
 73997 &:= (F(7) + ((F(3!) \times F(9))^{9-7})) \\
 74016 &:= (((7! + F((4! - 0!))) - 1) + (F(6)!)) \\
 74017 &:= ((7! + F((4! - 0!))) + ((1 + 7)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 74018 := ((7! + F((4! - 0!))) + (1 + 8!))
 74024 := ((7! × (F(4)!)) + (F(F(F(((0! + 2)!)))) × 4))
 74038 := -((F((F(7) + F(4))) - F((0! + ((3 × 8))))))
 74039 := ((7 × F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (-0! + F((F(3) × 9))))
 74042 := (((-F(7)) × (((F(4)! - 0!)) + F(4!)) × 2)
 74044 := -(((F((F(7) + F(4))) - F((0! + 4!))) - (F(4)!))
 74045 := ((7 + F((4! + 0!))) - F((F(F((F(4)!)) - (5))))
 74046 := -(((F((F(7) + F(4))) - F((0! + 4!))) - F(6))
 74048 := (F(7) × (((F(4)! - F((F(04)!)) × 8))
 74058 := ((-7) + F((4! + 0!))) - (5! × 8))
 74064 := (7! + (4! × ((0! - 6!) × (-4)))
 74065 := (F((((7 - F(4))! + 0!)) - ((F(6) × 5!))
 74066 := -(((F(F(7)) - F((4! + 0!))) - (-6 - 6!))
 74072 := -(((F(F(7)) - F((4! + 0!))) + ((7 - F(2))!))
 74083 := (-F(7) - (F((F(4)! × (-0! + (F(8)³))))
 74088 := (((7 × 4!) × F(08)) × F(8))
 74093 := ((F(F(7)) × (-4)) + F((-((0! - F(9))) - F(3!)))
 74094 := ((F(F(7)) × (F(4)!)) × (F((0! + 9)) - F(F(4))))
 74128 := ((-((7!/F(4))) + F(F(F(((1 + 2)!)))) × 8)
 74136 := ((-((7!/F(4)) - 1)) + F(F(F(3!)))) × F(6)
 74144 := ((7 + (F(F(((4 - 1)!))^{F(4)})) × F((F(4)!))
 74145 := ((F(((7 - 4)!))! - (F((-1 + F(F((F(4)!)))) × (-5)))
 74147 := (((F(7) × F((F(4)!)) - 1) × ((F(4)! - F(7))
 74147 := (((F(7) × F((F(4)!)) - 1) × ((F(4)! - F(7))
 74158 := (F(7) - ((F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 1)) × (-5)) - 8!))

 74160 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 0
 74161 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 1
 74162 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 2
 74163 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 3
 74164 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 4
 74165 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 5
 74166 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 6
 74167 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 7
 74168 := (F(7) × F(F(4)! - 1) × 6! + 8

$$\begin{aligned}
 74169 &:= (F(7) \times F(F(4)!) - 1) \times 6! + 9 \\
 74173 &:= (((7! + ((F(4)!)!) + 1) \times F(7)) - (3!)) \\
 74178 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(4!) - (-((1 - 7)))!)/8)) \\
 74184 &:= (((-7!)/(F(4)!) - 1) + F((F(8) + (4)))) \\
 74185 &:= ((-7!)/(F(4)!) + F((-1 + F(8)) + (5))) \\
 74235 &:= ((-F(7)) + ((F(4)!)!) \times (F(2^3) \times 5)) \\
 74238 &:= (((7 \times (F(4)!) + 2)^3) - F(F(8))) \\
 74241 &:= (-((7 \times 4)^2) + F((4! + 1))) \\
 74253 &:= (((F(7) \times (-4)) + F(25)) - 3!) \\
 74256 &:= ((-F(7)) \times (F(4)!) \times ((F(2) - 5!) \times F(6))) \\
 74263 &:= (((F(7) \times F((F(4)!)!) - F(2)) \times (6! + F(F(3)))) \\
 74264 &:= (((F(7) \times F((F(4)!)!) \times (F(2) + 6!)) - ((F(4)!)!) \\
 74266 &:= ((7 \times (F((F(4)!)!)!) - ((-2) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 74272 &:= ((F(7) - F((F(F((F(4)!)!) - F(2)))) \times (-F(7) - 2)) \\
 74284 &:= (((-F(7)) + F((4! + F(2)))) - 8) - ((F(4)!)!) \\
 74294 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times ((F(4) + 2)!) - F(9)) + F(4!)) \\
 74296 &:= (F((F(7) + (4!/2))) - (9 + 6!)) \\
 74298 &:= ((-F(7)) + F((4! + F(2)))) - ((F(9) \times F(8))) \\
 74299 &:= ((-7) - ((F(4)!)!) - (-F(2) - F((F(9) - 9)))) \\
 74304 &:= (((-7) + (F(4)!) - 3!) + F((0! + 4!)) \\
 74305 &:= (F(((7 \times 4) - 3)) - ((0! + (5)))!) \\
 74306 &:= ((F(((7 \times 4) - 3)) + 0!) - 6!) \\
 74308 &:= ((F((F(7) \times F(F(4)))) - (F(3!)!) - F(-((0! - F(8)))) \\
 74312 &:= ((7 - ((F(4)!)!) + (F(((3! - 1)^2))) \\
 74313 &:= ((7 + F((4! + F(F(3)))) + (1 - 3!)) \\
 74314 &:= (((F(7) - (4)) - 3!) + F((1 + 4!)) \\
 74315 &:= ((-F(7)) + F(4!)) - (F(F((3! + 1))) \times (-5!)) \\
 74318 &:= ((F(7) - ((F(4)!)!) + F(((3 + 1) + F(8)))) \\
 74321 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F(F(4)) \times F(F(3!)))^{2+1})) \\
 74323 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) + ((F(F(3!)) \times 2)^3)) \\
 74324 &:= (((F(7) + (F(4)!) - 3!) + F((F(2) + 4!)) \\
 74326 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(4))) + F((F(F(3)) + (-((2 - 6)))!)) \\
 74327 &:= (((F(7) \times 4!) + 3!) + F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 74328 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-4!)) - 3!) - (-2 \times 8!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 74333 := (((7 + F((4! + F(F(3)))))) - (3!)) + F(F(3!)))
 74334 := (((F(F(7)) × ((F(4) + F(3)))!) + 3!) + F(4!))
 74335 := ((7 + F(4!)) + (F(F((F(F(3)) + 3!))) × 5!))
 74336 := (((7 + 4!) + (F(F(3!))³)) × F(6))
 74338 := ((F(F(7)) × (F((4 × 3) + F(3))) + 8!)
 74339 := ((F(((7 × 4) - 3)) - 3!) + F(9))
 74340 := ((7!/F((F(4))!)) × (-F(3) + ((4 + 0!)!))
 74341 := (((-F(F(7))) - (F((F(4))!))!) × (-F(3))) - F((F(F((F(4))!)) - 1)))
 74342 := (((F(7) + 4!) - 3!) + F((4! + F(2))))
 74343 := (((-F(7)) - (F((F(4))!))!) × (-3)) - (((F(4))!^{3!}))
 74344 := (((7 × (F(4))!)³) + (4⁴))
 74346 := (((F(7) × (F(4))^{F(3!)}) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(F(6))))
 74347 := ((F(7) × (F(4))^{F(3!)}) - F((F(4) × 7)))
 74347 := ((F(7) × (F(4))^{F(3!)}) - F((F(4) × 7)))
 74348 := (((F(7) × (F(4))^{F(3!)}) + F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(8)))
 74353 := (((-7) × (F((F(4))!))!)/3! + F((5 + F(F(3!))))))
 74354 := (((7^{F(F(4))}) - 3!) + F((5^{F(F(4))})))
 74355 := (((F(7) - ((F(4))!))! × F(F(3!))) × (-5) + 5!)
 74359 := (-F(F(7))) - ((-F(4) × (F(3))!) + F((-((5 - 9))!)))
 74360 := -(((F(F(7)) + F(4!)) - ((3 × (F(6))!) + 0!)))
 74362 := -(((F(F(7)) + F(4!)) - (3 × ((F(6))! + F(2))))
 74365 := ((F(F(7)) + (4! × F((-3!) + F(F(6)))))) × 5
 74368 := (-7) × ((F(4!)/F((F(3) × 6))) - F(F(8)))
 74373 := (F(7) × ((F(4))^{F(3!)}) - ((7!/3!)))
 74375 := (((7! - 4) × 3) - F(F(7))) × 5
 74376 := (7! + ((F(4))! × (F((F(3) + F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))))
 74377 := (-((7⁴)) + ((F(F(F(3!))) - (7!)) × F(7)))
 74383 := -(((F(F(7)) + F(4!)) + ((F(3!) + 8!) × (-3)))
 74384 := ((F(F(7)) + F(4!)) - (-3) × (F(8)^{F(4)}))
 74386 := (F(7) × (((4 - 3!) × (-8)) - 6))
 74393 := (F(F(7)) - (((F(4) × 3!) × (-F(9))) - 3!))
 74395 := ((-7!)/F((F(4))!)) + F((F(F(3)) + ((9 - 5)!))
 74403 := ((-7!)/F((F(4))!)) + ((F((4! + 0!)) + F(3!)))
 74404 := ((7 + 4) × (-F(F(F(4)))) + F((-0! + F(F((F(4))!))))))

- 74408 := $(-(7) + ((F(4) + F((F(4))!)) \times F(-(0! - F(8))))))$
- 74413 := $-((F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) - (F((4! + 1)) - F(3))))$
- 74414 := $-(((F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(4)))) - F((1 + 4!))))$
- 74416 := $((-7!)/F((F(4))!)) + ((F((4! + 1)) + F(F(6))))$
- 74423 := $-((F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) - (F((4! + F(2))) + F(3!))))$
- 74424 := $((7 \times 4!) \times (((F(4))!)! - F(2)) - F(4!))$
- 74425 := $-((((((7 - 4))!)! - F((4! + F(2)))) - 5!))$
- 74426 := $((F(7)^{F(4)} - F((F(4))!)) \times F((F(2) + F(6))))$
- 74428 := $(F(7) + ((F(4) + F((F(4))!)) \times F(-(F(2) - F(8))))))$
- 74429 := $((-7!)/F((F(4))!)) + (F((4! + F(2))) + F(9))$
- 74432 := $((-F(F(7))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (4!)))) + (3!/(-2))$
- 74433 := $((F(7) \times (((F(4))!)! \times F((F(4))!)) + F(F(3!))) - (3!))$
- 74434 := $((7 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - 4)) - (3! \times F(4)))$
- 74435 := $((7! \times F(4)) - F(F((4 + 3)))) \times 5$
- 74436 := $-(((F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) - F((4! + F(F(3)))))) - (F(F(6))))$
- 74437 := $((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - (-4 \times (-3 + 7!)))$
- 74438 := $(7 \times (-((4! \times F((4 + 3)))) + F(F(8))))$
- 74440 := $(((-F(F(7))) \times F((F(4))!)) + F(4)) \times (-40)$
- 74442 := $((-7) - (4! \times 4!)) + F((4! + F(2)))$
- 74443 := $((F(7) \times (((F(4))!)! - 4) \times F((F(4))!)) - F(F(3!)))$
- 74444 := $((((-7!) + (F(4))!) \times (-4!)) - F(4!)) - 4$
- 74445 := $((((F(7) + ((F(4))!)! - (4!)) \times F(F((F(4))!))) \times 5)$
- 74447 := $((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(4))) + (4 \times 7!))$
- 74447 := $((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(4))) + (4 \times 7!))$
- 74448 := $-((7! + (F(4) \times ((4!^{F(4)}) - 8!)))$
- 74449 := $((7 + 4) \times F((4! - 4))) + F(9)$
- 74452 := $((7 \times F(F((F(4))!))) - (((F(4))!)! - F((5^2))))$
- 74456 := $((F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) \times (((F((F(4))!)!)/5! - F(6)))$
- 74458 := $((7! + F((F(4))!)) \times (-F(F(4)) - 5!))/8$
- 74461 := $((7 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - ((F(4) \times 6!) + 1))$
- 74462 := $((F(7) \times F((F(4))!)) \times (-4 + 6!)) - 2$
- 74463 := $((F(7) \times F((F(4))!)) \times (-4 + 6!)) - F(F(3))$
- 74464 := $((F(7) \times (4 + 4)) \times (6! - 4))$
- 74465 := $((-7) - F(4!)) - ((-F(4)) \times (F(6))! + 5!))$

$$\begin{aligned}74466 &:= (7! - (((F(4!)/4) - F(F(6))) \times (-6))) \\74467 &:= (-((F(7)^{F(4)})) + (((F(4)! + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7)) \\74472 &:= (((7! \times 4!) - F(4!)) - ((7 - 2)!)) \\74473 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + (4 \times (7! + 3!))) \\74474 &:= (((F(7) \times F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(F(4))}) - F((F(7) - F(4)))) \\74475 &:= ((F((F(7) + F(4))) + (F(4)!)) \times 75) \\74477 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) - (-4 \times (7! + (7)))) \\74481 &:= ((7 + 4) \times ((F(4)! + F((F(8) - 1)))) \\74484 &:= (((F(7) \times F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(F(4))}) - (F(8) + 4!)) \\74485 &:= ((F(7) - F(4!)) + (((F(4) \times 8!) - 5!)) \\74486 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F(4) \times (-8 + 6!)) \\74487 &:= (((F(F(7)) + (4!)) - F(4!)) \times (-F(8)) / F(7)) \\74488 &:= (((F(7)^4) + F(4!)) - (F(8) \times F(8))) \\74489 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((-4!) + (F(4!) / F(8))) \times F(9)) \\74492 &:= ((-7) - F((4! - 4))) \times (-9 + 2)) \\74493 &:= (((7! / (F(4)!)) - F(4)) \times F((9 + F(3)))) \\74494 &:= (((-((F(7)^{F(4)})) + (F(4)!)) \times (-F(9))) \times F(F(F(4)))) \\74495 &:= (-F(7)) - ((F(4!) / (-4!)) + (9! / (-5))) \\74496 &:= (((7! \times 4!) - F(4!)) - (96)) \\74497 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 4)) - (9 \times F(F(7)))) \\74508 &:= (((F(7) \times F(F((F(4)!)))^{F(F(5-0!))}) - (F(8))) \\74522 &:= (-7) + ((F(F((F(4)!)) \times F((5 + 2)))^2)) \\74523 &:= (((F(7) \times F((F(4) + 5)))^2) - 3!) \\74527 &:= (-F(F(7))) + (((F(4)! + 5!) \times F((-2) + F(7)))) \\74529 &:= (((-7) \times (F(4) - 5!))^2) / 9 \\74530 &:= (((F(7) \times F((F(4) + 5)))^{F(3)}) + 0!) \\74534 &:= ((F(F(7)) - ((F(4)! + 5!) \times F((5^F(3)) - 4)) \\74535 &:= (((7 + 4) \times F((5! / 3!))) + 5!) \\74536 &:= (((F(F(7)) - F(4!)) / (-5)) \times F(3!)) + (6!)) \\74542 &:= -(((F(7) - (4! \times 5!)) \times (4! + 2)) \\74543 &:= (((F(F(7)) - ((F(4)! + 5!) \times F((4! + F(F(3)))))) \\74544 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(4))) \times 5! + F(4!)) - (4!)) \\74545 &:= (F(((7 - F(F(4))) \times 5)) + (-4 \times 5!)) \\74546 &:= (((F(F(7)) - ((F(4)! + 5!) \times F((5^F(4)))) + F(6))\end{aligned}$$

$$74547 := (((-(F(F(7))) \times F((F(4))!)) \times (-5!/F(4)))) - F(7))$$

$$74547 := (((-(F(F(7))) \times F((F(4))!)) \times (-5!/F(4)))) - F(7))$$

$$74552 := (7 + ((-4) \times 5!) + F((5^2)))$$

$$74553 := -(((F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) - ((F((5 \times 5)) - 3!))))$$

$$74560 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 0$$

$$74561 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 1$$

$$74562 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 2$$

$$74563 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 3$$

$$74564 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 4$$

$$74565 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 5$$

$$74566 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 6$$

$$74567 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 7$$

$$74568 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 8$$

$$74569 := F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 5 \times F(6) + 9$$

$$74573 := (F(F(7)) - (((F(F(4)) - 5!) \times 7!)/F(3!)))$$

$$74574 := ((-F(7)) - F(4!)) + (-5) + (7! \times 4!))$$

$$74578 := (((7!/4) \times 5!) + (-7) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$74582 := (((-(F(F(7))) \times F((F(F(4)) + (5)))) + 8!) \times 2)$$

$$74584 := ((-F(7)) - F(4!)) + (5 + (8! \times F(4)))$$

$$74591 := (((7! \times 4!) - F((-((5 - 9))!)) - 1)$$

$$74592 := (-7) \times (4! - (5! \times F((9 + 2))))$$

$$74593 := (((-(F(7)) \times ((F(4))!)) \times 5) + F((F(9) - F(3!))))$$

$$74594 := ((7 - F(4!)) + (-5) + (9!/F(4)))$$

$$74597 := (((7! \times 4!) + (5)) - F((-9) + F(7))!))$$

$$74604 := (F(7) + (((F(4) \times (F(6))!) - 0!) - F(4!)))$$

$$74605 := ((F(7) - F(4!)) - (-((F(6))!) \times F(-((0! - (5))))))$$

$$74606 := ((7 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + ((F(6))!/(0! - F(F(6))))$$

$$74607 := (((F(F(7)) \times F(4)) + ((F(6) - 0!)!) \times F(7))$$

$$74608 := (((F(7) \times ((F(4))!)) - F((F(6) + 0!))) \times 8)$$

$$74613 := (((7! \times 4!) + F(F(6))) - F(((1 + 3))!))$$

$$74614 := (((7! \times 4!) + F(F(6))) + 1) - F(4!))$$

$$74620 := (F(7) \times (((F(4))!) \times F(6)) - (20))$$

$$74624 := (((7! - (4^{F(6)})) \times (-2)) - F(4!))$$

- 74626 := (((-F(7)) × F(4!)) / (-F(6))) + (- (2) - 6!))
- 74627 := ((7! + (F((F(4))!))!) - (F((F(F(6)) - 2)) × (-7)))
- 74628 := (((-F(7)) × F(4!)) / (-F(6))) - (-((2 - 8))!)
- 74630 := ((-F(7)) + (F(4!) / F(F(6)))) × F((F(3!) + 0!))
- 74632 := (- (7!) + (F((F(4))!) × (F(F(F(6))) - F((F(3!) × 2))))))
- 74633 := (-F(7)) × (((F(F(4)) - (6!)) × F(3!)) + 3)
- 74634 := ((((-F(7)) × F(4!)) / (-F(6))) - 3!) + (F(4)!)
- 74636 := (((F(7))! / F(F(4))) / (F(6))!) - F((3 × 6)))
- 74639 := ((F(7) - F(4!)) - (((F(6))! × (-3)) - F(9)))
- 74640 := ((-7) × F((4 + 6))) + F((4! + 0!))
- 74641 := ((-7) - F(((F(4))! + F(6)))) + F((4! + 1))
- 74642 := -((F((7 × F(F(4)))) - (-6 + F((4! + F(2))))))
- 74644 := ((F(7) × 4) - (((F(6))! × (-F(4))) + F(4!)))
- 74645 := ((-F(F(7))) + (F(F((F(4))!)) × (6! + F(F(4)))) × 5)
- 74646 := (- (7!) - ((-((F(4)^{F(6)}) × (F(4))!) - (F(6))!))
- 74647 := (((F(7) × 4!) × 6!) / F(4)) - F(F(7)))
- 74647 := (((F(7) × 4!) × 6!) / F(4)) - F(F(7)))
- 74648 := (((7^{F(4)}) - 6!) + F((4 + F(8))))
- 74653 := (F(F(7)) + (F(-(((F(4))! - F(F(6)))))) × (5! + F(3))))
- 74655 := ((7 - F(((F(4))! + F(6)))) + F((5 × 5)))
- 74657 := ((7! × 4) - ((F(F(F(6))) × (-5)) + F(F(7))))
- 74662 := (7 × (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((F(6))! / F((6 × 2))))))
- 74664 := (7! - (((4 × 6!) + F(F(6))) × (-4!)))
- 74666 := ((F(7) × ((F(F(4)) - (6!)) × (-F(6)))) - 6)
- 74672 := (F(7) × ((F(F(4)) - (6!)) × (-7 - F(2))))
- 74674 := (((F(7)^{F(4)}) × (F(F(6)) + F(7))) - (4!))
- 74683 := (((F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) × F((F(6) + 8))) / 3)
- 74685 := ((F((-7) + 4!)) + (F(6))!) + (8⁵)
- 74694 := (((F(7)^{4! / F(6)}) × F(9)) - (4))
- 74695 := ((((-7) + ((F(4))!)) × (-F(F(6)))) + F(9)) × (-5))
- 74697 := ((((-F(F(7))) - F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(9)) × 7)
- 74700 := (((-((F(7))!) / (F((F(4))!))!) + (7!)) / (- (0! + 0!)))
- 74703 := ((7 × (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (F((F(7) + 0!)))) + (3!))
- 74704 := (7 × (((F(F((F(4))!)) × (-F(7))) - 0!) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 74714 &:= (((-F(7)) \times (F(4))!) - F(F(7))) + F((1 + 4!)) \\
 74718 &:= (((F(7) \times F(4!)) - (7!)) / (1 \times 8)) \\
 74724 &:= (F(7) \times (((F(4))!)! - (-7!) + (2 \times (F(4))!))) \\
 74733 &:= ((-7) \times F(F((F(4))!))) + ((F(7) \times F(3!)) \times 3!!) \\
 74734 &:= (((-7) + 4!) \times 7!) - F((-3) + 4!)) \\
 74736 &:= (((-7!) + F(4!)) / (-7)) - (-F(3) \times (F(6))!) \\
 74737 &:= (((7! - (4 + 7)) + 3!!) \times F(7)) \\
 74738 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 4!) + (7!)) \times 3!) + F(F(8)) \\
 74740 &:= (((F(7) \times (-4)) - F(F(7))) + F((4! + 0!))) \\
 74743 &:= (-((7^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(7)))) + F((4! + F(F(3)))) \\
 74744 &:= ((-F(F(7))) \times F((F(4))!)) + ((7! \times (F(4))!) + F(4!)) \\
 74746 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) / (-F(7))) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(6))!)) \\
 74747 &:= (((-7!) / (F(4))!) \times (-F((7 + 4)))) - F(7) \\
 74747 &:= (((-7!) / (F(4))!) \times (-F((7 + 4)))) - F(7) \\
 74748 &:= (7! - (((F((F(4))!)! + 7) \times (-F(F(4)))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 74749 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - ((F(F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + 9)) \\
 74754 &:= (((7 \times F((4 + 7))) \times 5!) - (F(4))!) \\
 74755 &:= (((7 \times F((4 + 7))) \times 5!) - (5)) \\
 74758 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (F(F(7)) \times F((-((5 - 8))!))) \\
 74759 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-F(4) \times (F(7) - 5!))) - F(9)) \\
 \\
 74760 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 0 \\
 74761 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 1 \\
 74762 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 2 \\
 74763 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 3 \\
 74764 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 4 \\
 74765 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 5 \\
 74766 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 6 \\
 74767 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 7 \\
 74768 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 8 \\
 74769 &:= 7! \times F(4 + 7) / 6 + 9 \\
 \\
 74771 &:= ((-F(F(7))) - F(F((F(4))!))) + (F(((F(7) + F(7)) - 1))) \\
 74773 &:= (F(7) + ((F((4 + 7)) \times 7!) / 3!)) \\
 74776 &:= (F(((7 - 4))!) \times (-F(7) - (F(7) \times 6!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74783 &:= (((F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) \times F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-F(3)))) \\
 74784 &:= (((7 - F(4))!) \times (7! + 8)) - F(4!) \\
 74785 &:= (((-7) - F(4!)) - F(F(7))) + F((F(8) + (5))) \\
 74786 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - F((4! - ((7 - 8)))))) + 6)) \\
 74788 &:= (-7) \times (F((F(4))!) + ((F(F(7)) - F(F(8))) + (F(8)))) \\
 74789 &:= ((7 \times ((-4!) - F(F(7))) + F(F(8)))) - F(9) \\
 74790 &:= (-((F(F(7)) + F(F(4)))) + F((((F(7) - 9))! + 0!))) \\
 74792 &:= ((-F(7)) + F((4! + (7)))) / (9 \times 2) \\
 74793 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((4! - F((7 + 9))) / (-3))) \\
 74794 &:= (((F(7) + (F(4)^7)) \times F(9)) - (F(4))!) \\
 74796 &:= (((-F(7)) \times (F(4))!) \times (-F(7) \times F(9))) + (F(6))! \\
 74798 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) - F(((F(7) - 9) + F(8)))) \\
 74799 &:= (((F(7) - (F(4))!) - F(F(7))) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\
 74802 &:= (F(7) \times (((F(4))!) \times 8) - ((0! + 2))!) \\
 74804 &:= ((F(7) \times (4 - F(8))) + F((0! + 4!))) \\
 74807 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F(4))!) \times (80 + F(F(7)))) \\
 74808 &:= (((F(7) \times ((F(4))!)!) - (8 + 0!)) \times 8) \\
 74813 &:= (-((F(F(7)) - F((4 + F(8)))))) + F(F(((1 \times 3))!)) \\
 74814 &:= ((-F(F(7))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F(8) + F((1 + 4!))) \\
 74815 &:= (-((7!/4!)) + F((F(8) - ((1 - 5)))) \\
 74816 &:= (((F(7) \times ((F(4))!)!) - 8) \times F((1 \times 6))) \\
 74823 &:= (((F(F(7)) + (4!)) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(2) + 3!)) \\
 74824 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F(4) \times 8!) - F(2))) - F(4!)) \\
 74825 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(4!)) + (8! \times (-2 - 5))) \\
 74828 &:= (F(7) \times (-4) + (((8 - 2))! \times 8)) \\
 \\
 74830 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 0 \\
 74831 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 1 \\
 74832 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 2 \\
 74833 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 3 \\
 74834 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 4 \\
 74835 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 5 \\
 74836 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 6 \\
 74837 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 7 \\
 74838 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74839 &:= 7 \times (-F(F(4))^8 + F(F(F(3!)))) + 9 \\
 74840 &:= ((7 - (4! \times 8)) + F((4! + 0!))) \\
 74841 &:= (F(7) \times (-F(4)) + (8 \times (((4 - 1)!))) \\
 74842 &:= ((F(7) \times (((F(4)! \times 8) - F(4))) + F(2)) \\
 74843 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(4!)) - ((-8!) - (F(4)! \times 3)) \\
 74844 &:= (((7!/F(4)) + F(8)) \times 44) \\
 74845 &:= ((((-7) + ((F(4)!)) \times F(8)) - 4) \times 5) \\
 74846 &:= ((F(7) + F((4 + F(8)))) - (4! \times F(6))) \\
 74849 &:= ((-((7!/4!)) + F((F(8) + (4)))) + F(9)) \\
 74851 &:= (((7! - F((F(4)!)))/8) \times (5! - 1)) \\
 74852 &:= -(((F(F(7)) - F((4 + F(8)))) - (5!/2))) \\
 74854 &:= (F(7) \times ((48 \times 5!) - F(F(4)))) \\
 74856 &:= (((F(7) \times ((F(4)!)) - (8 - 5)) \times F(6)) \\
 74859 &:= (((-F(7)) \times ((F(4)!)) \times (-8)) - F(F((F(-((5 - 9))))))) \\
 74860 &:= (((-F(7)) \times ((F(4)!)) \times (-8)) - (F(F(6)) - 0!)) \\
 74863 &:= (-((F(F(7)) - ((F(4!)/8) \times 6))) + (F(3)!)) \\
 74864 &:= ((-7!) - ((F(4)!)) + ((8! - F(6)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 74865 &:= ((-7) + ((F(4)!)) \times (-((F(8) - (6)) - 5!))) \\
 74866 &:= (((-F(7)) \times ((F(4)!)) \times (-8)) - (F(6) + (6))) \\
 74867 &:= ((-7) - (F(4)!)) + ((8 \times 6!) \times F(7)) \\
 74869 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (4! - F(F(8)))) - (6!))/(-F(9))) \\
 74873 &:= (-7!) - (((F(F(4)) \times (-8!)) + 7) + 3!) \\
 74874 &:= (((7! \times 4!)/F(8)) \times F(7)) - (F(4)!)) \\
 74875 &:= (((7! \times 4!)/F(8)) \times F(7)) - (5) \\
 74876 &:= ((-7) + F(4)) + ((8 \times F(7)) \times 6!) \\
 74877 &:= (-((7 - 4)) + ((8! \times F(7))/7)) \\
 74879 &:= (((-F(7)) \times ((F(4)!)) \times (-8)) - F(-((7 - 9)))) \\
 \\
 74880 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8!/F(8) + 0 \\
 74881 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8!/F(8) + 1 \\
 74882 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8!/F(8) + 2 \\
 74883 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8!/F(8) + 3 \\
 74884 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8!/F(8) + 4 \\
 74885 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8!/F(8) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74886 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8! / F(8) + 6 \\
 74887 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8! / F(8) + 7 \\
 74888 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8! / F(8) + 8 \\
 74889 &:= F(7) \times F(4) \times 8! / F(8) + 9 \\
 \\
 74890 &:= (((-F(7)) \times ((F(4))!)!) \times (-8)) + (9 + 0!) \\
 74893 &:= (F(7) + ((-4) \times (8 - F(9))) \times 3!!) \\
 74896 &:= (((F(7) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - F((8 + 9))) \times F(6)) \\
 74897 &:= (7! + ((F((F(4))!) \times F(F(8))) - (F((9 + F(7)))))) \\
 74898 &:= ((F(7) \times ((F(4)!)/8) - F(9)) - 8) \\
 74904 &:= (((-F(7)) \times ((F(4))!)!) \times (-9 + 0!)) + (4!) \\
 74905 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) + (0 - 5!)) \\
 74906 &:= (F(7) \times (F(F(4)) + ((9 - 0!) \times 6!)) \\
 74907 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((F(9) + 0!) \times 7))) \\
 74914 &:= -((((7 - F(F(4))))!) + (-9 - F((1 + 4!)))) \\
 74928 &:= (((-7) \times 4!) \times F(9)) - (-2 \times 8!) \\
 74931 &:= (((F(7)^{F(4)}) \times F(9)) + F(F((3! + 1))) \\
 74933 &:= ((-F(7)) + (((F(4))! + F(9))^3)) + F(F(F(3!))) \\
 74934 &:= ((((-7!)/F(4))!) \times (-F(9))) + 3! + F(4!) \\
 74935 &:= ((7 + F(4!)) + (F(9) \times (3!! + 5!))) \\
 74937 &:= (((F(7)^{F(4)}) \times F(9)) + 3!) + F(F(7)) \\
 74940 &:= (-F(7)) - ((F((F(4))!) \times 9) - F((4! + 0!))) \\
 74941 &:= ((-7) \times (F(4) + 9)) + F((4! + 1)) \\
 74942 &:= (-((74 + 9)) + F((4! + F(2)))) \\
 74943 &:= ((7 - F((F(F(4)) + 9))) + F((4! + F(F(3)))) \\
 74945 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(4!)) + ((9!/F(4)) + 5!)) \\
 74946 &:= (((F(7)^4) + 9) + F(4!)) + F(6) \\
 74947 &:= ((-F(7)) \times (F(4))!) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7))) \\
 74947 &:= ((-F(7)) \times (F(4))!) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7))) \\
 74951 &:= (-74) + F((((9 - 5))! + 1)) \\
 74953 &:= ((F(((7 - 4))!) \times (-9)) + F((5^{F(3)})) \\
 74954 &:= (-(((F(7) + 4!) + F(9))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) \\
 74955 &:= (((7! \times F(4)) - 9) - 5!) \times 5 \\
 74956 &:= (((7^4) - (9!/(-5))) - F(F(6))) \\
 74958 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(4))! + (((F((9 - 5)))!)! \times 8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74965 &:= (F(7) - (((F(4!) \times (-F(9)))/F(F(6))) + 5!)) \\
 74967 &:= ((((-7!)/F(F(4))) \times (-F(9))) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \\
 74969 &:= ((-7) \times F((F(4)!)) + F(((9!)/(F(6)! + F(9)))) \\
 74970 &:= (-F((F(7) - F(4)))) + F((((9) + F(7))! + 0!)) \\
 74976 &:= (((F(7) \times 4!) \times F(9)) \times 7) + 6! \\
 74983 &:= ((-7) \times (F(4)!)) + F((9 + (8 \times F(3)))) \\
 74984 &:= (F(7) \times ((4! + (9!/F(8)))/F(4))) \\
 74988 &:= -(((F(7) + 4!) - F(((9 + 8) + 8)))) \\
 74990 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) - (F(9) + 0!)) \\
 74994 &:= ((-7) - 4!) + F(((9/9) + 4!)) \\
 74998 &:= (((7 - F(4!)) - F(9)) + F((F(9) - 8))) \\
 74999 &:= (((7 - 4!) - 9) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\
 75004 &:= ((-F(7)) - F((5 + 0!))) + F((0! + 4!)) \\
 75006 &:= ((-F(7)) + F((5^{0!+0!})) - 6) \\
 75009 &:= ((-7) + F((5^{0!+0!})) - 9) \\
 75011 &:= ((-F(7)) + F((5^{0!+1})) - 1) \\
 75013 &:= (-((7 + 5)) + F((0! + ((1 + 3)!))) \\
 75014 &:= ((-((7 + 5)) + 0!) + F((1 + 4!))) \\
 75018 &:= (-7) + F(((5 - 0!) + F((1 \times 8)))) \\
 75023 &:= (F((F(7) + ((5 + 0!) \times 2))) - F(3)) \\
 75024 &:= (-F((7 - 5))) + F((0! + (24))) \\
 75027 &:= ((7 - 5) + F(-((0! - (2 \times F(7))))) \\
 75033 &:= (F((75/03)) + F(3!)) \\
 75036 &:= ((F(7) \times ((5 + 0!)!) + (3! \times F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 75037 &:= ((7 + 5) + F(-((0! - (F(3) \times F(7))))) \\
 75040 &:= ((7 + F((5 + 0!))) + F((4! + 0!))) \\
 75041 &:= ((F(7) + F((5 - 0!))) + F((4! + 1))) \\
 75042 &:= (((F(7) + (5)) - 0!) + F((4! + F(2)))) \\
 75043 &:= ((F(7) + (5)) + F(((0! + (4))^{F(3)})) \\
 75044 &:= ((F(7) + F((((5 \times 0)! + 4!))) + (F(4)!)) \\
 75046 &:= (F((F(7) - (5))) + F((0! + (4 \times 6)))) \\
 75047 &:= (((7 \times 5) + F((0! + 4!))) - F(7)) \\
 75048 &:= (((7 - 5) + F((0! + 4!))) + (F(8))) \\
 75053 &:= ((-7) \times (-5 + 0!)) + F((5^{F(3)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75059 &:= (F(((F((7+5)) + 0!) - 5!)) + F(9)) \\75064 &:= ((F(7) \times F((5-0!))) + F((F(F(6)) + 4))) \\75088 &:= ((-(F(7) \times 5!) + F(F(08))) \times 8) \\75099 &:= ((75 - 0!) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\75114 &:= (F(((7+5) - 1)) + F((1+4!))) \\75132 &:= (-((F(7) - 5!)) + F(((-1 + 3!)^2))) \\75138 &:= ((-7) + 5!) + F((1 + (3 \times 8))) \\75144 &:= (((-7) + 5!) + F((1+4!))) + (F(4)!) \\75145 &:= (F(-((75/(1-4)))) + 5!) \\75146 &:= (((-7) + 5!) + F((1+4!))) + F(6) \\75148 &:= ((F((7+5)) + F((1+4!))) - (F(8))) \\75149 &:= (((F(7) + 5!) + F((1+4!))) - 9) \\75152 &:= ((7+5!) + F(((1 \times 5)^2))) \\75153 &:= (((7+5!) + 1) + F((5^{F(3)}))) \\75158 &:= ((F(7) + 5!) + F((-((1-5)) + F(8)))) \\75194 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F((5+1)))) - (F(9) \times (F(4)!))) \\75224 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F((F(2) + F((F(4)!)))) \\75233 &:= (-((F(F(7)) - F((5^2)))) + (F(F(3!))^{F(3)})) \\75234 &:= ((-7) + F((5^2))) + (3!^{F(4)}) \\75240 &:= ((F(7) + (5)) \times (F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!)))) - 0!)) \\75243 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) + (F(4)!) - F(F(3!))) \\75244 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F((F(4)!)) - (F(4)!) \\75250 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) - F((5+0!))) \\75252 &:= -((F(7) - ((5! \times 2) + F((5^2)))) \\75264 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^2))) + ((6 - F(4))!) \\75270 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((F((5^2)) + F(7)) - 0!)) \\75278 &:= ((F(7) + F((5^2))) + (7!/F(8))) \\75280 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F((5^2)) + F(8)) + 0!))) \\75282 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F((5^2)) + ((8/2)!)) \\75296 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (F((5^2)) + (9!/6!)))) \\75306 &:= ((-F(7) + ((5 \times 3!) - 0!)) \times F(F(6))) \\75327 &:= ((-F(7) + (5 \times 3!)) \times F((F(2) + (7)))) \\75328 &:= (-((F(7) - 5!)) \times (3! - (2 \times 8))) \\75333 &:= (((7! \times 5) - F((3 + F(3!)))) \times 3)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75334 &:= (7 \times ((-5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(3)^{F(4!)})) \\75335 &:= (F(7) \times (((5 + 3!!) \times F(3!)) - (5))) \\75336 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 5!) + (((3!^3) + 6!)) \\75337 &:= -((F(F(7)) - ((5 \times 3)) \times (F(3) - 7!))) \\75339 &:= (((-F(7)) \times F(((5 - F(F(3))))!)) / (-F(3!))) - 9 \\75340 &:= ((-7!) / (5 - F(F(3!)))) + F((4! + 0!)) \\75344 &:= ((7! \times (5 \times 3)) - (4^4)) \\75346 &:= (((F(7) - 5!) \times (-3)) + F((4 + F(F(6)))) \\75348 &:= ((F((F(7) + (5))) / F(3!)) + F((4 + F(8)))) \\75353 &:= (-((7^5)) + ((F(3!) + 5!) \times 3!)) \\75354 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F((5^{F(3)}))) + ((5! - 4!)) \\75361 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(((5 - F(F(3))))!) / F(6)) + 1)) \\75362 &:= (-7!) + (((5! - F(F(3))) - (F(6)!) \times (-2)) \\75364 &:= (-7!) - (((5! - F(3)) - (F(6)!) \times F(F(4)))) \\75365 &:= (-((7! - 5))) - (-F(3) \times ((F(6)!) - 5!)) \\75367 &:= ((7! \times (5 \times 3)) - F((6 + 7))) \\75372 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (-5) \times ((3 \times 7!) + F(2)))) \\75373 &:= (((7! \times (5 \times 3)) - F(F(7))) + 3!) \\75374 &:= (-7!) - (((-5!) - (F(3)!) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))) \\75378 &:= ((F(F(7)) + 5!) + F((-((3 - 7)) + F(8))) \\75383 &:= (((7 + 5!) + 3!) \times F((8 + 3))) \\75384 &:= (((F(7) \times 5!) \times F(3)) + F(8)) \times 4! \\75387 &:= (-F(7)) - ((5 + 3!!) \times (-8) \times F(7)) \\75388 &:= -((F(F(7)) + (((5 \times 3!!) \times (-F(8))) - (F(8)))) \\75396 &:= (((7! \times (-5)) / F(3)) + F(9)) \times (-6) \\75398 &:= (-F(7)) - (((-5) \times 3!!) + 9) \times F(8) \\75399 &:= (((F(F(7)) + 5!) + F(F(3!))) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\75404 &:= (7! + ((5! - F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!))) \times (-4))) \\75408 &:= (((F(7) \times (-5) - ((F(4)!)!) - 0!) \times (-8)) \\75413 &:= (F(7) \times (5 - ((F(4!) \times (-1)) / F(3!))) \\75424 &:= (((F(7) + 5!) \times F(4)) + F((F(2) + 4!))) \\75426 &:= -((F(7) \times (5! + (F((4^2)) \times (-6)))) \\75432 &:= (-((7! + 5!)) + ((4! - (F(3)!)!) \times (-2))) \\75433 &:= (((-F(7)) - (-5!) \times ((F(4)!)!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - F(3!)) \\75434 &:= ((F(7) \times (5 + (F(4!) / F(3!)))) + F(F((F(4)!)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75435 &:= ((-(7! - 5)) + (F(4))!) \times (-3 \times 5)) \\75438 &:= (-F(7)) - ((-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) + (3 + F(F(8)))) \\75440 &:= (((-F(7)) - (-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 0! \\75441 &:= ((-F(7)) - (-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) - F(F(F(((4 - 1))!))) \\75442 &:= (((-F(7)) - (-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + F(2) \\75443 &:= ((-(F(7) - 5!)) \times ((F(4))!)!) - F((-4) + F(F(3!))) \\75444 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 54) - F((F(4))!)) \times (F(4))!) \\75446 &:= (7 \times (-((5! + 4!) + 4!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\75447 &:= (-7) + ((5! \times ((F(4))!)!) - F((F(4) \times 7))) \\75448 &:= (F((F(7) + 5))) + (((F(4))! \times (4!)!)/(F(8)!)) \\75452 &:= -(F(F((F(7) - 5))) + (((F(4))!)! \times (-5!) + 2)) \\75453 &:= (((F(7) - 5!) \times (-4)) + F(5^{F(3)})) \\75454 &:= (-F(F(((7 - 5) \times 4))) - (-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) \\75456 &:= (7 - (((-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) + 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\75458 &:= (((((F(7) - 5))! \times F((F(4))!))/5) + F(F(8))) \\75460 &:= (7 + (((5! \times ((F(4))!)!) - F(F(F(6)))) - 0!)) \\75461 &:= (7 + ((5! \times ((F(4))!)!) - F(F(F((6 \times 1))))) \\75462 &:= (7 - (((-5!) \times ((F(4))!)!) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(2)) \\75463 &:= (7 + (((5! \times ((F(4))!)!) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(3)) \\75464 &:= -((((F((F(7) + 5))) + 4) - (F(6))!) \times F(F(4))) \\75465 &:= (F(7) \times (F((5 \times 4)) - (F(6) \times 5!))) \\75466 &:= (F((F((7 - 5) + 4!)) + (F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)))) \\75467 &:= -((F(7) - ((-5) \times F(4)) \times (F(6) - 7!))) \\75468 &:= (-((7! + 5!)) - (F(F(4)) \times (6 - 8!))) \\75472 &:= (((7 \times 5!) + F((F(4))!)) \times F((F(7) - 2))) \\75474 &:= (((7! \times 5) - ((F(4))! \times 7)) \times F(4)) \\75478 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-5)) + F(F((F(4))!))) - (-7) \times F(F(8)))) \\75480 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 0 \\75481 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 1 \\75482 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 2 \\75483 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 3 \\75484 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 4 \\75485 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 5 \\75486 &:= -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$75487 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 7$$

$$75488 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 8$$

$$75489 := -7! - 5! + F(F(4)) \times 8! + 9$$

$$75491 := ((F(F(7)) \times (5! + ((F(4))! \times F(9)))) - 1)$$

$$75493 := ((F(F(7)) \times (5! + ((F(4))! \times F(9)))) + F(F(3)))$$

$$75494 := ((F(F(7)) \times (5! + ((F(4))! \times F(9)))) + F(F(4)))$$

$$75498 := (((7! \times 5!) - (4! \times F(9)))/8)$$

$$75512 := -(((F(F(7)) - F((5 \times 5))) - (((1 + 2))!))!)$$

$$75513 := -(((F(F(7)) - ((F((5 \times 5)) + 1))) - 3!!))$$

$$75533 := (((7! - 5) \times (5 \times 3)) + F(3!))$$

$$75534 := (((7! - 5) \times 5) + 3) \times F(4)$$

$$75535 := ((F(7) - (5! \times (5! + 3!))) \times (-5))$$

$$75537 := (((-(7 \times 5)) - 5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 7$$

$$75541 := -((F((F(7) + 5))) - (5^{F(4)!+1}))$$

$$75544 := ((7 + F((5 \times 5))) + (F((F(4))!)^{F(4)}))$$

$$75546 := (((7! - 5) \times 5) \times F(4) + F(F(6)))$$

$$75564 := (((7! \times 5!) - 5!)/F(6) - F(F((F(4))!)))$$

$$75568 := (-7) + (-5) \times (5 - (6! \times F(8)))$$

$$75583 := (((7! \times 5!) - 5!)/8 - F(3))$$

$$75584 := (((7! \times 5!) - 5!)/8 - F(F(F(4))))$$

$$75586 := (((7! \times 5!) - 5!) + 8)/F(6)$$

$$75587 := ((7! \times (-5 \times (5 - 8)))) - F(7)$$

$$75593 := (-7) - ((-5) \times ((F(-(5 - 9)))!)) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$75594 := -(((F((7 + 5)) - (5 \times 9!))/4!))$$

$$75600 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 00$$

$$75601 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 01$$

$$75602 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 02$$

$$75603 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 03$$

$$75604 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 04$$

$$75605 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 05$$

$$75606 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 06$$

$$75607 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 07$$

$$75608 := 7! \times 5!/F(6) + 08$$

- 75609 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 09
- 75610 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 00
- 75611 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 11
- 75612 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 12
- 75613 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 13
- 75614 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 14
- 75615 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 15
- 75616 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 16
- 75617 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 17
- 75618 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 18
- 75619 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 19
- 75620 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 00
- 75621 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 21
- 75622 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 22
- 75623 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 23
- 75624 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 24
- 75625 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 25
- 75626 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 26
- 75627 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 27
- 75628 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 28
- 75629 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 29
- 75630 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 30
- 75631 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 31
- 75632 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 32
- 75633 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 33
- 75634 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 34
- 75635 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 35
- 75636 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 36
- 75637 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 37
- 75638 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 38
- 75639 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 39
- 75640 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 40
- 75641 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 41
- 75642 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 42
- 75643 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 43

- 75644 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 44
- 75645 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 45
- 75646 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 46
- 75647 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 47
- 75648 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 48
- 75649 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 49
- 75650 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 50
- 75651 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 51
- 75652 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 52
- 75653 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 53
- 75654 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 54
- 75655 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 55
- 75656 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 56
- 75657 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 57
- 75658 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 58
- 75659 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 59
- 75660 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 60
- 75661 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 61
- 75662 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 62
- 75663 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 63
- 75664 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 64
- 75665 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 65
- 75666 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 66
- 75667 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 67
- 75668 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 68
- 75669 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 69
- 75670 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 70
- 75671 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 71
- 75672 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 72
- 75673 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 73
- 75674 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 74
- 75675 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 75
- 75676 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 76
- 75677 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 77
- 75678 := 7! × 5! / F(6) + 78

$$75679 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 79$$

$$75680 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 80$$

$$75681 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 81$$

$$75682 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 82$$

$$75683 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 83$$

$$75684 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 84$$

$$75685 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 85$$

$$75686 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 86$$

$$75687 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 87$$

$$75688 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 88$$

$$75689 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 89$$

$$75690 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 90$$

$$75691 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 91$$

$$75692 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 92$$

$$75693 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 93$$

$$75694 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 94$$

$$75695 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 95$$

$$75696 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 96$$

$$75697 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 97$$

$$75698 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 98$$

$$75699 := 7! \times 5! / F(6) + 99$$

$$75719 := (7 \times ((- (5!) + F(F((7 + 1)))) - 9))$$

$$75726 := (7 \times (-(((5! + (7)) + F(2))) + F(F(F(6))))))$$

$$75727 := ((7 + 5!) + ((F(7) + 2) \times 7!))$$

$$75732 := ((7 \times (-((5! + (7))) + F(F(F(3!)))))) - F(2))$$

$$75733 := (F(7) - (5! \times ((- (7!) - F(3!)) / F(3!))))$$

$$75734 := (-((7! - 5!)) - ((- (7) - (F(3!)!) \times F(F(4))))$$

$$75736 := ((-((F(7) - 5!)) - (- (F(7)) \times 3!)) \times F(6))$$

$$75739 := (F((F(7) + (5 + 7))) + (F(F(3!)) \times F(9)))$$

$$75740 := (7 \times ((-((5! + (7))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + 0!))$$

$$75743 := ((F((F(7) + (5 + 7))) - F(F(4))) + 3!)$$

$$75744 := (((7! - F((5 + 7))) \times (F(4)!)) + F(4!))$$

$$75746 := ((F((F(7) + (5 + 7))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (6!))$$

$$75747 := (((F(7) - (5)))! + ((7! + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 7))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75754 &:= (7 \times (F(F((-5) + F(7)))) - (5! + (4))) \\
 75756 &:= ((F(7) - 5!) \times ((7 + 5) - 6!)) \\
 75758 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((-5) + 7!) \times 5!)/8) \\
 75766 &:= ((F((F(7) + (5 + 7))) + F(F(6))) + (6!)) \\
 75768 &:= (((7! \times (-5))/(-7)) + F(6)) \times F(8) \\
 75769 &:= (((F(F(7)) + 5!) \times F(F(7))) + (6! \times (-9))) \\
 75774 &:= ((-7) + (5 \times (7! + F(7)))) \times F(4) \\
 75776 &:= ((7 \times (-5!) + F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) - 6) \\
 75781 &:= ((-7) \times 5!) + ((7 \times F(F(8))) - 1) \\
 75782 &:= (7 \times (-5!) + F((F(7) + F((8 - 2)))))) \\
 75783 &:= ((-7) \times 5!) + ((7 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(3))) \\
 75784 &:= ((-7) \times 5!) + ((7 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) \\
 75796 &:= (7 \times ((5! + (-7) \times F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 75803 &:= (7 \times ((-5!) + F(F(8))) + 03) \\
 75804 &:= (((7 \times (-5!) + F(F(8))) + 0!) + F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 75809 &:= ((7 \times ((-5!) + F(F(8))) - 0!) + F(9)) \\
 75816 &:= ((7 \times (-5!) + F(F(8))) + F((1 + F(6)))) \\
 75823 &:= (F(7) - ((-5) \times F(8)) \times (2 + 3!)) \\
 75824 &:= (7 \times ((-5!) + F(F(8))) + (2 + 4)) \\
 75827 &:= -((7! + ((5! + 8!) \times (-2)) + F(7))) \\
 75831 &:= (((7 - 5!) + F(F(8))) \times (3! + 1)) \\
 75832 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((5 \times F(8)) \times 3!) - F(2))) \\
 75833 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((5 \times F(8)) \times ((3 + 3)!)) \\
 75834 &:= (-((7! - ((5! + 8!) \times F(3)))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 75835 &:= -((7! - ((5! + 8!) \times F(3)) - (5))) \\
 75837 &:= (F(7) - (((-5!) + F(F(8))) + 3!) \times (-7)) \\
 75838 &:= (7 \times (((-5!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(3))) + 8) \\
 \\
 75840 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 0 \\
 75841 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 1 \\
 75842 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 2 \\
 75843 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 3 \\
 75844 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 4 \\
 75845 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 5 \\
 75846 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75847 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 7 \\
 75848 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 8 \\
 75849 &:= -7! + (5! + 8!) \times F(F(4)) + 9 \\
 \\
 75852 &:= (7 \times ((-5!) + F(F(8))) + (5 \times 2)) \\
 75857 &:= (75 + ((F(F(8)) - 5!) \times 7)) \\
 75857 &:= (75 + ((F(F(8)) - 5!) \times 7)) \\
 75863 &:= ((F(7) - 5!) \times ((8 - 6!) + 3)) \\
 75864 &:= ((7 \times (-5) + F(F(8)))) - (6! + F(4)) \\
 75866 &:= (7 \times ((-5!) + F(F(8))) + (6 + 6)) \\
 75867 &:= ((7 \times (-5) + F(F(8)))) - (((F(F(6))/7)!)!) \\
 75872 &:= (((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(8))) \times 7) - F(2)) \\
 75873 &:= (F(F(7)) - (-5 \times (8 + (7! \times 3)))) \\
 75874 &:= (((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(8))) \times 7) + F(F(F(4))) \\
 75880 &:= (7 \times (((-5) \times F(8)) + F(F(8))) - 0!) \\
 75882 &:= -((7! + ((5! + F(8)) + 8!) \times (-2))) \\
 75887 &:= (((7 - 5!) + F(F(8))) + 8) \times 7 \\
 75893 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((-((5 - 8))))!)))) - (9^3) \\
 75902 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(F(-((5 - 9))))!)))) - (((0! + 2)!)!) \\
 75903 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(F(-((5 - 9))))!)))) + (0! - 3!!) \\
 75915 &:= ((-7!) - F(F(F(-((5 - 9))))!)) \times (-15) \\
 75923 &:= (((7! \times 5!) + F((9 \times 2)))/F(3!)) \\
 75933 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(-((5 - 9)))^{F(3!)} - 3!!)) \\
 75936 &:= (((-7) + 5!) \times (F(9) - F(3))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 75943 &:= (7 \times ((5 - (F(9) \times F(4))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 75944 &:= ((7 \times ((F(-((5 - 9))))! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))))) - (((F(4)!)!)!) \\
 75947 &:= (-((75 \times 9)) + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) \times 7)) \\
 75964 &:= (7 \times ((-((5! - F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4)!)!)) \\
 75965 &:= ((7 \times (-((5! - 9)) + F(F(F(6)))))) + 5! \\
 75985 &:= (7 \times (((-5) + F(9)) + F(F(8))) - 5!) \\
 75999 &:= (((7!/5) - F(9)) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\
 76026 &:= ((-7!) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!)) \times (F(2) \times 6)) \\
 76033 &:= ((-7!) - (F(6)!) + F(-((0! - ((3^3)))))) \\
 76034 &:= (((-7!) - (F(6)!) + 0!) + F((F(3) + 4!)) \\
 76044 &:= (((7! - F((F(F(6)) + 0!))) - F(4)) \times (-F(4)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76045 &:= (-((F(F(7)) - 6) \times (0! + ((F((F(4))!))! / (-5!)))) \\
 76056 &:= (((-7!) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!))) + (5)) \times 6 \\
 76069 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((0! + (6! / (-9)))))) \\
 76128 &:= (F(7) \times ((6! + 12) \times 8)) \\
 76184 &:= (-((F(7) - ((6 - 1))!) \times (-8 + ((F(4))!))!) \\
 76195 &:= (7 \times (-(61) + F(F(F((F((9 - 5))!)))))) \\
 76214 &:= (((F(7) \times F(6)) + 2) \times (-1 + ((F(4))!))!) \\
 76223 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(F(6))) - 2) - F((2 + F(3!)))))) \\
 76226 &:= ((-F(F(7))) - F((F(F(6)) - 2))) - (-2) \times (F(6))!) \\
 76230 &:= ((7! / F(6)) \times (((2 + 3))! + 0!)) \\
 76233 &:= (((F(7))! / (F(6))!) / 2) - F((F(3) \times F(3!))) \\
 76234 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F((2 + F(3!)))))) - F(4) \\
 76238 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(2))) - (F((3! + 8)))) \\
 76240 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (6!)) \times (2 \times 40)) \\
 76243 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - 2) - F(((F(4))! + F(3!)))) \\
 76244 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (2 \times (4! + F(4)))))) \\
 76246 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(2)) - F(((F(4))! + F(6)))) \\
 76254 &:= (((7! / F(6)) \times (F(2) + 5!)) + 4!) \\
 76262 &:= ((7 \times F(F((6 + 2)))) + (6! / (-2))) \\
 76263 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((-2) + 6!) / F(3)) \\
 76264 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (-2) + (6! / F(F(4)))) \\
 76266 &:= (((F(7) \times 6) \times F((2 \times F(6)))) - (6!)) \\
 76267 &:= ((((((F(7))! / (F(6))!) / 2) - (6!)) - F(F(7))) \\
 76267 &:= ((((((F(7))! / (F(6))!) / 2) - (6!)) - F(F(7))) \\
 76285 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(2) + (8! / 5!))) \\
 76293 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F((F(2) + 9)) - F(3!)))) \\
 76314 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!))) - (-1 + 4!))) \\
 76318 &:= -(((7! - 6!) + (F(3) \times (1 - 8!)))) \\
 76319 &:= ((F((7 + F(6))) \times 3!!) - (1 + 9!)) \\
 \\
 76320 &:= -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 0 \\
 76321 &:= -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 1 \\
 76322 &:= -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 2 \\
 76323 &:= -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 3 \\
 76324 &:= -7! + 6! + F(3)! \times 2 + 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$76325 := -7! + 6! + F(3!)! \times 2 + 5$$

$$76326 := -7! + 6! + F(3!)! \times 2 + 6$$

$$76327 := -7! + 6! + F(3!)! \times 2 + 7$$

$$76328 := -7! + 6! + F(3!)! \times 2 + 8$$

$$76329 := -7! + 6! + F(3!)! \times 2 + 9$$

$$76330 := (((7! + F(F(F(6)))) - (3!!)) \times (3! - 0!))$$

$$76332 := (-((7! - 6!)) - ((-3!) - (F(3!)!) \times 2))$$

$$76333 := (F(7) - (((F(6))! / (-3)) + 3!!) \times 3!))$$

$$76334 := (((-7) - (F(6))!) \times (-F(3))) - (3!! \times (F(4))!))$$

$$76335 := ((-7) - 6!) \times (-3 \times 35))$$

$$76336 := (-7!) - (((F(6))! + F(3!)) \times (-F(3))) - (6!))$$

$$76342 := (((7^6) - (F(3!)!) - (F(4^2))))$$

$$76343 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))}) - (3!!)))$$

$$76344 := (((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times 3!!) / F(F(4))) + (4!))$$

$$76345 := ((F(F(7)) + (F(F(6)) \times (3!! - 4))) \times 5)$$

$$76346 := (((-F(7)) - (F(6))!) \times (-F(3))) + ((F(4))! \times (-6!))$$

$$76347 := ((7 \times (-6) + F((-3) + 4!))) - F(F(7))$$

$$76349 := (F(7) \times ((6! + F(F(3))) + (F(4!) / 9)))$$

$$76351 := (((7! / F(6)) + F(F(3))) \times (5! + 1))$$

$$76353 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(3!)))) - (5! + F(3)))$$

$$76354 := (((7! + F(F(F(6)))) - (3!!)) \times 5) + (4!))$$

$$76355 := ((F((7 + F(6))) + 3!!) + F((5 \times 5)))$$

$$76356 := ((F(7) - 6!) \times ((3! - 5!) + (6)))$$

$$76362 := (((7 - 6!) \times 3) + (F(6))!) \times 2$$

$$76365 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((3! + F(6))) - 5!))$$

$$76370 := (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (37 - 0!)))$$

$$76373 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(3!) + F(F(7))) + F(3!)))$$

$$76374 := (((7! \times 6) - F(F(3))) - F(F(7))) + F(4!))$$

$$76375 := ((-F(7)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3!)!) \times F(7))) / (-5))$$

$$76376 := (((7^6) - 3!!) - F(F(7))) - (F(6))!$$

$$76381 := ((-F(F(7))) - F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(3!) \times (F(F(8)) - 1)))$$

$$76384 := (7 \times (((-6) \times 3!) + F(F(8))) + F(F(4)))$$

$$76388 := ((-((7! - 6))) \times (F(3!) - (F(8)))) + F(F(8))$$

$$76390 := (-F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(3) - 9)) + 0!))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76393 &:= (F(F(7)) + (((F(6))!/3) \times (-F(9)))/(-3!)) \\
 76394 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3! \times F(9)) + 4!)) \\
 76399 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(3!)) \times 9) + F(9))) \\
 76403 &:= (-F(F(7))) - ((F(F(F(6))) + F(F(4))) \times (-(0! + 3!))) \\
 76406 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (4! \times (0! + F(6)))) \\
 76412 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (4! + ((1 + 2)!))) \\
 76413 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((4! - F(13)))) \\
 76414 &:= (((F(7) \times (F(6))!)/(F(4))! - F(F(F((F((1 \times 4))))!)))) \\
 76418 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(4))! \times F((1 + 8)))) \\
 76422 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F((4! + F(2)))) - F(2)) \\
 76423 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + F((4! - ((2 - 3)))) \\
 76424 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((-6) + 4!)^2) + (4)) \\
 76426 &:= (((F(7) \times F(6)) + F(F(4))) \times (F(2) + 6!)) \\
 76427 &:= ((((-7!) + (F(6))!)/(F(4))! - F(2)) \times F(7)) \\
 \\
 76430 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 0 \\
 76431 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 1 \\
 76432 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 2 \\
 76433 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 3 \\
 76434 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 4 \\
 76435 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 5 \\
 76436 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 6 \\
 76437 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 7 \\
 76438 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 8 \\
 76439 &:= 7 \times F(F(F(6))) - 4! \times F(3!) + 9 \\
 \\
 76440 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 0 \\
 76441 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 1 \\
 76442 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 2 \\
 76443 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 3 \\
 76444 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 4 \\
 76445 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 5 \\
 76446 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 6 \\
 76447 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 7 \\
 76448 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76449 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)) - 4!) + 9 \\76451 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (4!))) - F((5 - 1))) \\76452 &:= (-F(7)) + ((6! \times F(F(4))) + F((5^2))) \\76453 &:= (F(7) + (((F(6) + ((F(4))!)) \times 5) \times F(F(3)))) \\76454 &:= (7 \times (F((6 + (F(4) \times 5))) - (4!))) \\76455 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(4))!)) + (-5 - 5!)) \\76456 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (4!))) + F((-5 + F(6)))) \\76459 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (6!)) \times (-((F(4) + 5!) + F(9)))) \\76460 &:= -((F((F(7) + (6))) - ((F(F(4)) \times (F(6))! + 0!))) \\76461 &:= -((F((F(7) + (6))) - (F(F(4)) \times ((F(6))! + 1)))) \\76462 &:= -(((F((F(7) + (6))) - F(4)) + ((F(6))! \times (-2)))) \\76463 &:= -((F((F(7) + (6))) + ((F(F(4)) + (F(6))! \times (-F(3)))))) \\76465 &:= ((7! + F((F(F(6)) + 4))) - (6! \times 5)) \\76466 &:= ((7! + F(F(F(6)))) + ((4 \times F(F(6))) \times 6!)) \\76467 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(6)) \times 7)) \\76467 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(6)) \times 7)) \\76469 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((4! \times 6) + 9)) \\76470 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4))!)) - F((F(7) - 0!))) \\76472 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(4))! + F((F(7) - F(2)))))) \\76473 &:= (((7 + (F(6))!) \times F(F(4))) - F((F(7) + 3!))) \\76474 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((4! + F(7)) \times 4)) \\76475 &:= (((7! \times 6) + F(4!)) - (F(7) + 5!)) \\76477 &:= ((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (4! + (7! \times F(7))) \\76479 &:= (-F(F(7))) - (((F(F(F(6))) + F((F(4))!)) \times (-7)) - F(9)) \\76485 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((-4) + F(8) + 5!)) \\76487 &:= ((7 \times ((F(6) + (F(4))!) + F(F(8)))) - F(F(7))) \\76489 &:= (7 \times (((F(F(6)) - (F(4))!) + F(F(8))) - F(9))) \\76490 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (4 \times (F(9) - 0!))) \\76492 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(F((F(4))!)))) + (F(9)/2)) \\76495 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(F(4)) - (9 + 5!)))) \\76496 &:= (-7!) - (((-F(6)) \times F(4!))/9 - (F(6))!) \\76497 &:= (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4))!)) - (9 \times F(7))) \\76498 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(6)) \times F((F(4))!)) \times F(9) + F(F(8))) \\76499 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (4! + 99))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76500 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (((5! + 0!) + 0!))) \\
 76501 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((5! + 0!) \times (-1))) \\
 76502 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 + (0 \times 2)))!) \\
 76503 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5! - ((0 \times 3)))!) \\
 76504 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5! + 0!) - F(4))) \\
 76505 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F((5 - 0!)) - 5!))) \\
 76509 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)) - F(F((5 + 0!)))))) + F(9)) \\
 76518 &:= (F(7) \times ((-6!) - F(((5 - 1)!)) / (-8))) \\
 76523 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5! - F(2^3))) \\
 76524 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5! + 2) - 4!)) \\
 76526 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5! - (-((2 - 6)))!)) \\
 76530 &:= (((-F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (5 + F(3))) - 0! \\
 76532 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times ((5! \times 3) + F(2))) \\
 76534 &:= -((F((F(7) + F(6))) + (-5!) \times (3^{F(4)!}))) \\
 76535 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)) + (5))) - (F(3) + 5!)) \\
 76536 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5! - F((3 + 6)))) \\
 76537 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)) + (5))) - (-((F(3) - (7))))!) \\
 76539 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5! - 3) - F(9))) \\
 76543 &:= (((-F(7)) - (F(6)!)) \times 5) + (F(4!) \times 3!) \\
 76544 &:= ((7! \times (F(F(6)) - (5))) - (4^{F(4)!})) \\
 76545 &:= ((7! / (F(F(6)) - (5))) \times (F(4)^5)) \\
 76557 &:= (-F(F(7))) - ((F(F(F(6))) + (5! / 5)) \times (-7)) \\
 76561 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((6! / 5!)))) - 61) \\
 76567 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((-5) + 6!) / F(7)) \\
 76567 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((-5) + 6!) / F(7)) \\
 76575 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 + (7! / 5!))) \\
 76578 &:= ((76 - 5!) - (-7) \times F(F(8))) \\
 76579 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)) - (5))) - F((F((F(7) - 9))))!) \\
 \\
 76580 &:= 7 \times (-F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8)) + 0 \\
 76581 &:= 7 \times (-F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8)) + 1 \\
 76582 &:= 7 \times (-F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8)) + 2 \\
 76583 &:= 7 \times (-F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8)) + 3 \\
 76584 &:= 7 \times (-F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8)) + 4 \\
 76585 &:= 7 \times (-F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8)) + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$76586 := 7 \times (- (F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 6$$

$$76587 := 7 \times (- (F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 7$$

$$76588 := 7 \times (- (F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 8$$

$$76589 := 7 \times (- (F(6) - 5)! + F(F(8))) + 9$$

$$76595 := ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - (5))) + F((F((9 - 5))))!$$

$$76596 := (((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5)) - F(F(((9 - 6))))!$$

$$76598 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((5 - 9) + 8))!$$

$$76600 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) + (00)))!$$

$$76602 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) - ((0 \times 2))))!$$

$$76603 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (6 + F((0! + 3))))$$

$$76604 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (- (6) + (04)))!$$

$$76605 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) + ((0! - (5)))))$$

$$76608 := (((7^6) - 6!) - 0!) - 8!$$

$$76609 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(6) - ((0 \times 9))))!$$

$$76610 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((6 + 1)) - 0!))$$

$$76611 := (((7!/6!) \times F(F(F(6)))) - 11)$$

$$76614 := (((7! \times 6) + (6)) + F(((1 \times 4))))!$$

$$76621 := (((7!/6!) \times F(F((6 + 2)))) - 1)$$

$$76623 := (((7!/6!) \times F(F((6 + 2)))) + F(F(3)))$$

$$76624 := (((7! \times 6) + (F(6) \times 2)) + F(4!))$$

$$76627 := (((((F(7))! / (F(6))!) - (6!)) / 2) - F(F(7)))$$

$$76629 := (((7!/6) + F(F(6))) \times F((2 + 9)))$$

$$76630 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 0$$

$$76631 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 1$$

$$76632 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 2$$

$$76633 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 3$$

$$76634 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 4$$

$$76635 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 5$$

$$76636 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 6$$

$$76637 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 7$$

$$76638 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 8$$

$$76639 := (F(7) - 6) \times F(F(F(6))) + F(3!) + 9$$

$$76640 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6!/40))$$

- 76641** := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((-6) + 4!) + 1)$
76642 := $((((7! + (6)) \times 6) + F(4!)) - 2)$
76643 := $((((7! + (6)) \times 6) + F(4!)) - F(F(3)))$
76644 := $((7! + (6)) \times ((6 - F(4))!) + F(4!))$
76645 := $((F(F(7)) + ((6! \times F(F(6))) - (4!))) \times 5)$
76646 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (((6 \times 4)/6)!)$
76647 := $((F(F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (((F(6)!/(F(4))!) \times (-F(7))))$
76648 := $((F(7) \times F(6)) \times ((6! - (4)) + F(8)))$
76650 := $(7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(6) - (5)) + 0!)))$
76654 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) + 5!)/4)$
76657 := $((7!/F(F(6))) + (F((6 + 5)))) \times F(F(7)))$
76658 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (6 \times (-((5 - 8))!))$
76664 := $((((7! + F(6)) \times 6) + F(6)) + F(4!))$
76670 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(6) \times (7 - 0!)))$
76675 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-67) + 5!)$
76683 := $((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(6) + F(F(8))) \times 3!))$
76684 := $((7!/6!) \times (F(6) + F(F(8)))) + (F(4)!)$
76686 := $((7!/6!) \times (F(6) + F(F(8)))) + F(6)$
76687 := $(F(7) \times (((F(6)!/(-F(6))) + F(F(8))) - 7))$
76690 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (69 - 0!))$
76694 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-((6 - 9) \times 4!))$
76695 := $((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(6))) + (9 + 5!))$
76696 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((6!/9) - (6)))$
76703 := $((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 0!))) - 3)$
76704 := $(((((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) - 0!) - F((F(4))!))$
76705 := $((((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) - F((0! + (5))))$
76706 := $((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(7) + 0!) \times 6))$
76707 := $((((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + ((0! - (7))))$
76713 := $((F(7) + F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times (1 + 3!))$
76721 := $((((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + F(((2 + 1)!))$
76723 := $((((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + (2 + F(3!)))$
76728 := $((F(F(7)) + (((6! \times F(7)) - 2))) \times 8)$
76733 := $(((((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + F(F(3!))) - F(F(3)))$
76734 := $(-7) \times ((F(6) - F((7 \times 3))) - 4!)$
76735 := $((F(F(7)) + (-6) + (7! \times 3)) \times 5)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76736 &:= (((-((F(7) \times 6!)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(3))) \times (-F(6))) \\
 76737 &:= (((F(F(7)) + (6! \times F(7))) \times F(3!)) - 7) \\
 76738 &:= ((((-7!) - F(F(6))) \times (-F(7))) - F(F(3))) + F(F(8))) \\
 76739 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((7 + 3!) \times 9)) \\
 76740 &:= ((F(7) \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((7! + F(4)))))) + 0!) \\
 76741 &:= (((F(7))! / (6! \times 7!)) + F((4! + 1))) \\
 76742 &:= ((7 \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) + ((F(4) + 2)!)) \\
 76743 &:= ((-7) - F(F(F(6)))) + (-7!) + (F(4!) \times F(3))) \\
 76744 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (6! \times F(7))) \times (4 + 4)) \\
 76745 &:= ((7 \times F((F(6) + F(7)))) + ((F(4) + 5!)) \\
 76746 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times 6) + ((-F(7)) \times F(4!)) / (-F(6))) \\
 76748 &:= ((F((F(7) + (6))) \times (7 \times 4)) - 8!) \\
 76749 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (7 + (-((4 - 9))!)) \\
 76750 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((7 + 5!) + 0!)) \\
 76753 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(7) + 5!) - F(3))) \\
 76756 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((-7) + 5!) + F(F(6))) \\
 76757 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) - (F((-5) + F(7)))) \\
 76763 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(6)) + F((F(7) + F(6)))))) - 3! \\
 76764 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) - (F(6) + (F(4))!)) \\
 76765 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F(6) + F(7)) \times 6!)) \times 5) \\
 76768 &:= (-7!) - ((-6!) + F((F(7) + F(6)))) \times (-8)) \\
 76770 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) - (7 + 0!)) \\
 76771 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) - (7 \times 1)) \\
 76772 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) - (7 - F(2))) \\
 76774 &:= (((7! - F((F(6) + F(7)))) \times (-F(7))) - 4) \\
 76778 &:= (F(7) \times ((6! \times (-7)) + F((F(7) + 8)))) \\
 76779 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) + F(-((7 - 9))) \\
 76782 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-F(7))) + (8/2)) \\
 76784 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F(6) - 7!)) \times (8 - 4!)) \\
 76785 &:= (7 - ((F(F(F(6))) - (7!)) \times (-8 + 5))) \\
 76786 &:= ((F(7) \times ((6! \times (-7)) + F(F(8)))) + F(6)) \\
 \\
 76790 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9!)) + 0 \\
 76791 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9!)) + 1 \\
 76792 &:= 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9!)) + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$76793 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 3$$

$$76794 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 4$$

$$76795 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 5$$

$$76796 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 6$$

$$76797 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 7$$

$$76798 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 8$$

$$76799 := 7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(7) - 9)!) + 9$$

$$76803 := ((7 \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) + F((0! + F(3!))))$$

$$76804 := (7 \times ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) + (0! + (4))))$$

$$76805 := ((7 \times ((F(6) + F(F(8))) + 0!)) + 5!)$$

$$76813 := (F(F(7)) + ((-6) + F(F(8))) \times (1 + 3!))$$

$$76814 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (8 \times ((1 \times 4)!))$$

$$76824 := ((7 \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) + F((2 + F((F(4)!))))$$

$$76826 := ((F(F(7)) + (-6) \times F(8)) \times (-2 + 6!))$$

$$76833 := ((7 \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) + (F(3)^{3!}))$$

$$76835 := ((-7) \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(8)))) - (-3 \times 5!)$$

$$76838 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(8) + 3!) \times 8))$$

$$76841 := (((F(F(7)) - 6) \times 8) + F((4! + 1)))$$

$$76842 := ((-F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) - (-F(8) \times F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 2))))$$

$$76843 := ((7 \times ((F(6) + F(F(8))) + (4!))) - 3)$$

$$76844 := ((7 \times ((F(6) + F(F(8))) + (4!))) - F(F(4)))$$

$$76845 := (((F(7) + 6!) \times F(8)) - 4!) \times 5)$$

$$76847 := (((F((7 + F(6))) \times F(8)) \times (F(4)!)) - F(7))$$

$$76854 := ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (8 \times (5 + 4!)))$$

$$76856 := (((7! - 6) - F(F(8))) \times (-5 - F(6)))$$

$$76864 := (((F(7)! / (F(6)!)) + (8 - 6!)) / F(F(4)))$$

$$76873 := (F(7) - (F(F(6)) \times (-F((8 + 7)) \times 3!)))$$

$$76875 := (((F(7) + 6) + F(F(8))) \times 7) + 5!)$$

$$76876 := (((7! / 6!) \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(6))$$

$$76880 := ((F(F(7)) + ((6! + 8))) \times 80)$$

$$76882 := ((-((7! - F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times F((8 - F(2))))$$

$$76888 := ((7^6) - ((F(8) \times F(8)) + 8!))$$

$$76894 := (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(6))) + ((8! - 9))) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$76896 := (((F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times F((F(8) - 9))) + (F(6)!))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76902 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(9) + ((0! + 2)!))) \\
 76912 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(6))) + ((9 - 1)!) \times 2) \\
 76914 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (6 \times F((9 + 1)))) + (4!)) \\
 76923 &:= (7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((F(9) + F(2)) + F(3!)))) \\
 76924 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(9))) + (2^{F(4)!})) \\
 76925 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) + 9)) - (-2 \times 5!)) \\
 76934 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F((9 - F(3))) \times 4!)) \\
 76936 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 9)) + (F((3! + F(6)))) \\
 76944 &:= (((7! \times (F(F(6)) + F(9))) - F(4!))/F(4)) \\
 76946 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (6!)) \times (F(9) - (4! \times F(6)))) \\
 76947 &:= (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) - (9 + 4)) \times (-F(7))) \\
 76958 &:= (7 \times (((F(6) \times (-9)) + 5!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 76964 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (9 \times 6))) + ((F(4)!)!)) \\
 76965 &:= ((F(7) + 6!) \times (-((9 + 6)) + 5!)) \\
 76975 &:= ((7 \times F(F(F((-((6 - 9)!)!)))) + ((F(F(7)) + 5!))) \\
 76984 &:= (((7 \times F(F(6))) \times (-9)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)!)) \\
 76985 &:= ((7 \times (69 + F(F(8)))) - 5!) \\
 76986 &:= ((F(7) \times (-((6 - 9)!) \times F((8 + F(6)))) \\
 76987 &:= (((F(7)!) / F(-((6 - 9))) / 8!) - F(F(7))) \\
 76994 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(9))) + F((-9 + 4!))) \\
 77033 &:= (-7) - ((-F(7)) + (-((0! - 3)!) \times (-3!))) \\
 77038 &:= (F(7) \times ((-((7! + 0!)) + F(F(3!))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77049 &:= (7 \times ((70 + F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) - 9)) \\
 77053 &:= (F(7) + (-((F(7) - (05!)) \times 3!)) \\
 77063 &:= ((7 \times F(F((7 + 0!)))) + ((F(F(6))^{F(3)})) \\
 77064 &:= ((F(7) \times (F((7 + 0!) + (6!))) \times F((F(4)!)!)) \\
 77087 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) - 0!) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 77088 &:= ((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) + (-((0! - 8)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 77093 &:= (F(F(7)) - (7 \times ((0 - F(9)) - F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 77098 &:= (7 \times ((F(7) + F((0! + 9))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77133 &:= (7 \times ((71 + F(3)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 77134 &:= ((7 \times F(F((7 + 1)))) + (F(3!)^{F(4)})) \\
 77154 &:= (7 \times ((71 + 5) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) \\
 77183 &:= ((7! \times F((7 + 1))) - F((F(8) + F(3))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77186 &:= (((7! \times F(7)) + F(F((1 \times 8)))) + (6!)) \\
 77193 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (((7 - 1)!)) \times (9^{F(3)})) \\
 77207 &:= (-F(7) + (((F(7))!/2)/((0! + (7))))!) \\
 77213 &:= (-7) + (((F(7))!/2)/(F((1 \times 3)!)))! \\
 \\
 77220 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 0 \\
 77221 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 1 \\
 77222 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 2 \\
 77223 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 3 \\
 77224 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 4 \\
 77225 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 5 \\
 77226 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 6 \\
 77227 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 7 \\
 77228 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 8 \\
 77229 &:= F(7)!/((7 + F(2))! \times 2) + 9 \\
 \\
 77232 &:= (F(7) - (((F(7))!/(-2))/(F(3)!)) + F(2)) \\
 77233 &:= (F(7) + ((F(7))!/(2^3)! \times F(3))) \\
 77234 &:= (F(7) - (((F(7))!/(-2))/(F(3)!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 77238 &:= (7 \times (((F(7) - 2) \times F(3!)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77243 &:= ((7 \times (F((F(7) - 2)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) - F(3) \\
 77244 &:= (((F(7))!/7! \times (2^4)) + (4!)) \\
 77248 &:= (7 + (((F(7))!/2)/(F((F(4))!))! + (F(8)))) \\
 77254 &:= (((7! \times (-7))/2) \times (-5)) - F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 77273 &:= (F(F(7)) - (-(((7 - 2)! - F(7))) \times 3!)) \\
 77286 &:= ((7 \times ((-7) - F(2)) + F(F(8)))) + (6!) \\
 77293 &:= ((7 \times (-7) + F(F(-(F(2) - 9)))))) + (3!)) \\
 77294 &:= (7 \times ((7 + F((2 + 9))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) \\
 77316 &:= (-((F(7) - (7^{3!}))) - (F((1 \times 6))!)) \\
 77322 &:= ((-7) + (7^{3!}) - (F((F((2 + 2))!))!)) \\
 77323 &:= ((-7) + ((7^{3!}) + F(2))) - (F(3!))! \\
 77324 &:= ((-7) + ((7^{3!}) + 2)) - (F((F(4))!))! \\
 77328 &:= (((7 \times 7)^3) - F(2)) - 8! \\
 77329 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(7))) - (3!! \times (2 - F(9)))) \\
 77330 &:= (((7 \times 7)^3) - (F(3!))! + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}77332 &:= (- (7!) - (((7! \times 3!) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-2))) \\77333 &:= ((7 + ((7^{3!}) - 3)) - (F(3)!))! \\77334 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(7)) - 3!!) + F((F(F(3)) + (4!)))) \\77335 &:= (- (7) + ((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (3! \times 5!))) \\77336 &:= (((7 \times F((7 \times 3))) - 3!) + 6!) \\77337 &:= (- (F(7)) + (((F(7) \times F(3!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 7)) \\77338 &:= (7 + (((7^{3!}) + F(3)) - 8!)) \\77341 &:= (((7 \times F((7 \times 3))) + ((F(4)!))!) - 1) \\77342 &:= ((7 \times F((7 \times 3))) + ((4 + 2)!)) \\77343 &:= (((7 \times F((7 \times 3))) + ((F(4)!))!) + F(F(3))) \\77344 &:= (((7 + (F(7)^{F(3)}))^{F(F(4))}) + F(4!)) \\77345 &:= ((F(7) + (F(((7 - 3)!)/F(4))) \times 5) \\77346 &:= (((7 \times F((7 \times 3))) + (4)) + 6!) \\77348 &:= (((F(7) + (7^{3!})) + (F(4)!)) - 8!) \\77349 &:= (7 + ((7 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (-((F(4) - 9)!))) \\77350 &:= (7 \times ((F(7) \times F(3!)) + F(F(F((5 + 0!)))))) \\77353 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((F(F(7)) - F(F(3!))) + 5!)) - 3) \\77354 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((F(F(7)) - F(F(3!))) + 5!)) - F(F(4))) \\77357 &:= ((F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + (F(F(3!)) \times 5)) \times 7) \\77362 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-7)) - F(3!)) + (F(6)!)) \times 2) \\77363 &:= (((7 \times F((7 \times 3))) + F(F(6))) + 3!!) \\77364 &:= ((((-F(7)) - F(F(7))) \times (-3!)) \times F(F(6))) + F(4!)) \\77365 &:= ((7 \times (F((F(7) - F(3))) + F(F(F(6)))))) + 5! \\77368 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((F(7) \times (3! + 6!)))) \times 8) \\77369 &:= (- (7) - ((- (7) \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (6! + F(9)))) \\77378 &:= (((7! - F(F(7))) + 3!!) \times (- (7) + F(8))) \\77382 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-7)) + (F(3) + 8!)) \times 2) \\77383 &:= ((7 \times (7 + F(F(F(3!)))))) + (- (8) + 3!!) \\77384 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-7)) + (3 + 8!)) \times F(F(4))) \\77385 &:= (7 \times ((- ((F(7) - F(3))) + F(F(8))) + 5!)) \\77386 &:= ((7 \times ((F(F(7)) - F(F(3!))) + F(F(8)))) - (6!)) \\77392 &:= (7! - ((7 + F(F(3!))) \times (-F((9 \times 2)))) \\77413 &:= (7 \times ((- (7) + ((4 + 1)!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\77424 &:= (((- (7!)) + F(F(7))) + F((4! - 2))) \times (F(4)!)) \\77426 &:= ((7 \times ((F(7) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - F(2))) + (6!))\end{aligned}$$

- 77427 := $(7 \times ((-F(7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + (2^7))$
- 77432 := $(((-7) - F((-7) + 4!)) + (F(3)!)) \times 2$
- 77433 := $((7 \times (F(7) + F((4! - 3)))) + 3!!)$
- 77434 := $((7 \times (F(F(7)) - 4) - (F(3)!)) \times (-F(F(4))))$
- 77435 := $(-F(7) - (7 \times ((F(F(4)) - F(F(F(3)))) - 5!))$
- 77436 := $((7! \times 7) / F(4) + (3! \times F(F(F(6))))$
- 77439 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(F(7))) - ((F(4)! / (-F(3))) + F(9)))$
- 77442 := $(-7! - (F(F(7)) \times ((F(4)! + (((F(4)!)! / (-2))))))$
- 77443 := $(F(F(7)) + (7 \times ((4 \times F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(F(F(3!))))))$
- 77446 := $((7! - 7) \times 4 + F(4!)) + F(F(F(6)))$
- 77448 := $(7 \times ((7! + F(4!)) - (4! + 8!))$
- 77449 := $(-F(7) + (7 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (-((4 - 9)!))))$
- 77450 := $(-F(7) - ((-7) \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 5!)) - 0!)$
- 77453 := $(F(F(7)) - (((F(7)! / F(F(4))) / (-((5 + 3)!))))$
- 77454 := $((7 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) + 5!)) - F((F(4)!))$
- 77456 := $(7 + (((7^{F(4)!}) + 5!) - (F(6)!))$
- 77457 := $(-F(7) - (F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) \times (-5! + 7)))$
- 77461 := $((7 \times (((7 - F(F(4)))! + F(F(F(6)))) - 1)$
- 77462 := $(7 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) + ((6 - F(2))!))$
- 77463 := $((7 \times (((7 - F(F(4)))! + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))$
- 77464 := $(-7! - (((F(F(7)) \times (-4)) - (F(6)!)) \times F(F(4))))$
- 77467 := $((7! \times 7) + F(4!)) - F((6 + F(7)))$
- 77473 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(4!) / F(F((7 - 3))))$
- 77474 := $(F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))) + (F(4!) + (7! \times 4)))$
- 77475 := $(F(7) - (-7) \times (F((F(4) \times 7)) + 5!))$
- 77476 := $(-7! + (7 \times ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) / F(7)) + F(F(F(6))))))$
- 77480 := $(-((7! + 7!)) - (F((F(4)!)) \times (-F(F(8)) - 0!)))$
- 77483 := $(7 \times (F(F(7)) + ((F(4!) + 8!) / F(3!)))$
- 77484 := $(((((F(F(7)) + F(7)) \times F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4)!))$
- 77485 := $((F((7 + 7)) - (((F(4)!)! \times (-F(8)))) \times 5)$
- 77486 := $((-((7! + 7!)) - F(F(4))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(6)))$
- 77488 := $((7! / (-7) + F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 8$
- 77493 := $(F(7) \times ((-7! + F(-((4! - F(9)))) + F(F(F(3!))))))$
- 77496 := $((7 \times ((F(7) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 9)) + (6!))$
- 77497 := $(((((F(7) \times 7) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(9))) \times 7)$

- 77504 := (7 × (((7 + 5!) - 0!) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))))
 77518 := (7 × (((7 + 5!) + 1) + F(F(8))))
 77533 := ((7 × (F(F(7)) + F(F((5 + 3)))))) - 3!!
 77534 := (((7 - (F(7) × 5!)) + (F(3!)!)) × F(F(4)))
 77544 := ((-7!) - (((F(7))! / (-5)) / (F((F(4))!))!)) × F(4)
 77545 := (F(7) × ((F(F(7)) + (5! × F((F(4))!))) × 5))
 77546 := ((-F(7)) × (F(F(7)) + (5))) + (F(F(4)) × (F(6))!))
 77548 := (F(F(7)) - (7 × ((-5!) + F(F((F(4))!))) - F(F(8))))
 77553 := (7 × ((F(7) + 5!) + F(F((5 + 3))))))
 77560 := (7 × (((F(7) + 5!) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0!))
 77563 := ((F(7) × (-((7! - (5)))) + F(F(F(6)))) + (3!!))
 77574 := (((F(7) × F(7)) + (5⁷)) - ((F(4))!))
 77575 := (((7! / (-7)) - (5)) × (F(7) - 5!))
 77595 := ((7! - F((F(7) - (5)))) - (9! / (-5)))
 77597 := ((F(7) × (7 + 5!)) × (F(9) + F(7)))
 77611 := ((F(F(7)) × (-F(7))) - ((F(6))! × (-1 + 1)))
 77613 := ((F(F(7)) × (-F(7))) + (((F(6))! + 1) × F(3)))
 77623 := (-7) - (-7) × (F(F(F(6))) + F((2 × 3!)))
 77624 := (-((F((7 + 7)) × F(6))) - (-2) × (F((F(4))!))!))
 77632 := (((F(F(7)) × (-F(7))) + F(F(6))) - ((F(3))! × (-2)))
 77634 := (((7! - (7)) - 6!) × 3!) × F(4)
 77636 := (F(7) × (F(F(7)) + ((F(6) × 3!) - F(F(6))))))
 77644 := (7 × (((7! - (F(6))!) + F(4!)) + 4))
 77648 := (-7!) - ((-F((7 + F(6)))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) × (-8))
 77653 := ((7 × (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))))) - (-5! + 3!!)
 77658 := (7 × (((7 + F(F(6))) + 5!) + F(F(8))))
 77679 := -((7! - (((F(7) - 6!) × F(7)) × (-9))))
 77693 := (7 × ((F(F(7)) + (6! / (-9))) + F(F(F(3!))))))
 77695 := (-7) - ((-7) × F(F(F(6)))) - (9 × 5!))
 77697 := ((7! × (7 + F(6))) + (9 × F(F(7))))
 77714 := (7 × ((F(7) × (F(7) - 1)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))))
 77736 := (7! - (F(F(7)) × ((F(7) × (-3)) × F(6))))
 77744 := ((7! - (F(F(7)) × (-F(7) × 4!))) + F((F(4))!))
 77749 := (-7) × (F(F(7)) + ((7! / (-4)) × 9))
 77753 := (F(7) × (-((7! - 75)) + F(F(F(3!))))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 77763 &:= (7 \times (((F(7) \times F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 3!)) \\
 77765 &:= ((F((F(7) + F(7))) - (7! \times F(F(6)))) \times 5) \\
 77766 &:= (F(7) \times (-((7! - 76) + F(F(F(6))))) \\
 77784 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (7 + 7)) - (F(8))) \times 4!) \\
 77798 &:= (7 \times ((7 \times ((F(7) - 9))!) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77833 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (7 \times (F(8) + F(3)))) + (F(3)!))! \\
 77834 &:= (-7) + (((F(7) \times F(8)) + 3!)^{F(F(4))}) \\
 77844 &:= -((((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) - (8!/F(4))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 77847 &:= (((((F(7) \times F(7)) + F(F(8))) + (F(4)!)) \times 7) \\
 77854 &:= ((7! - F((7 + F(8)))) + (5^{F(F(4)!)})) \\
 77873 &:= (-F(F(7))) - (7 \times (-((F(F(8)) + F(F(7)))) + F(F(3!)))) \\
 77884 &:= ((-F(7) \times (F(F(7)) - (F(8)))) - (-8! \times F(F(4)))) \\
 77895 &:= ((7 \times ((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - F(9))) - 5!) \\
 77904 &:= (-7!) + ((F(F(7)) + F((9 + 0!)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 77935 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(9) \times 3))) - 5!) \\
 77938 &:= (-7) + (7 \times ((9 \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 77957 &:= ((-7) \times ((F(7) - 9))!) + (5^7) \\
 77974 &:= (F(7) \times (((7 \times F(9)) + 7!) + ((F(4)!))!)) \\
 77993 &:= (F(F(7)) - (((F(7) \times (-9)) + 9) \times 3!)) \\
 78035 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (-((F(8) + 0!) \times 3!)) \times (-5)) \\
 78054 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times F((8 - 0!))) + F((5^{F(F(4))})) \\
 78055 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((8! - (05)!)/5!)) \\
 78062 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - ((0 - 6!) \times 2)) \\
 78063 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + ((0! + (6! \times F(3)))) \\
 78064 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (-((0! + 6!) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 78078 &:= (F(7) \times (((F(8) + 0!) \times F(7)) \times F(8))) \\
 78133 &:= (((F(7) - 8)^{1+3!}) + F(3!)) \\
 78134 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + (((1 \times 3))!^{F(4)})) \\
 78146 &:= (((F(7) - 8)^{1+F(4)!}) + F(F(6))) \\
 78175 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(8)) - 1)) + (F(7) \times 5!)) \\
 78184 &:= (-(((7! - 8!) - F(18))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 78245 &:= (((F(7) - 8)^{F(2)+F(4)!}) + 5!) \\
 78247 &:= (((7! - 8) + F((2^4))) \times F(7)) \\
 78260 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + F(2)) \times (F(6) - 0!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}78264 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((F(8) \times 2) \times F(6))) - (4!)) \\78273 &:= (F(7) \times ((F((8 \times 2)) + 7!) - 3!)) \\78275 &:= (-(F(7)) - ((-8!) \times F((F(2) \times F(7))))/5!)) \\78279 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 8!)/(-(2-7)))! - 9) \\78295 &:= (7 - ((-8!) \times F(F(-(2-9))))/5!)) \\78297 &:= (((-F(7)) \times F(F(8))) \times 2) + (9! + F(7))) \\78302 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + (3!!/(0! + 2)))) \\78309 &:= -((7! - ((F(8)^3) \times 09))) \\78324 &:= ((((-7!) - F(F(8))) + F(3!)) \times (-2)) + F(4!)) \\78329 &:= (-7) + (((8 \times 3!)^2) \times F(9)) \\78333 &:= (((-7!) + F((F(8) + F(F(3)))))) \times 3) + (F(3!))! \\78334 &:= ((((-7!) - F(F(8))) + 3) \times (-F(3))) + F(4!)) \\78340 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 0 \\78341 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 1 \\78342 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 2 \\78343 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 3 \\78344 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 4 \\78345 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 5 \\78346 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 6 \\78347 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 7 \\78348 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 8 \\78349 &:= (7! + F(F(8))) \times F(3) + F(4!) + 9 \\78351 &:= (F(7) \times ((-8!) - F(F(3!))) + F(((5-1)!))) \\78352 &:= ((-((7 \times 8)) + 3!!) \times (5! - 2)) \\78353 &:= ((F(F(7)) + (F((8 \times F(3))) \times 5!)) - (F(3!))!) \\78357 &:= ((F(F(7)) - F((8-3!))) + (5^7)) \\78358 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(3) \times 5!) + 8))) \\78363 &:= (((7 + F(F(8))) \times F(3!)) - (F(F(6))^3)) \\78364 &:= (F(7) \times (((-8!) + F(F(3))) - F(F(6))) + F(4!)) \\78384 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-F(8))) - 3!) \times (8-4!)) \\78393 &:= (-7) + ((8!/F((3+9)))^{F(3)}) \\78399 &:= (7! - ((F(8) + 3!!) \times (-99))) \\78400 &:= ((7!/(F(8) - F(4)))^{0!+0!})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78407 &:= (((-((F(F(7)) + F(F(8)))) - F(F((F(4))!))) - 0!) \times (-7)) \\
 78416 &:= (F(7) \times ((-8!) + F(4!)) - 16) \\
 78424 &:= (((7!/(F(8) - F(4)))^2) + 4!) \\
 78432 &:= (((7! \times F(8)) - (4! \times F(F(F(3!)))))/(-2)) \\
 78433 &:= -((F(F(7)) + ((-8!) + F((4^{F(3)}))) \times F(3))) \\
 78435 &:= ((-7!) + (F(8) \times F((4^{F(3)})))) \times 5 \\
 78438 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) - (F(4)!) \times F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \\
 78443 &:= (-((F(7)^{F(8-4)})) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(3!)!)) \\
 78444 &:= ((7! + (F(F(8)) \times (F(4)!)) + (F(4!)/(F(4)!)) \\
 78445 &:= ((F(F(7)) + ((-8) \times F(4!))/(-4!)) \times 5 \\
 78446 &:= (((7 + 8!) \times F(F(4))) - (F(4!)/F(F(6)))) \\
 78449 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F((F(4))!) + F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)) \\
 78454 &:= (((F(F(7)) + (8^{F(4)})) \times 5!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 78456 &:= (-7!) - ((-((8^4) + 5!) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 78465 &:= ((F(7) \times (F((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))))) - (6!)) - 5!) \\
 78473 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4))!)) - F(7)) - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 78476 &:= (((F(7) + 8!) - F(4!)) \times (-F(7))) + F(F(6)) \\
 78478 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 8) - F((F(4))!)) - (-7) \times F(F(8))) \\
 78481 &:= (F(7) \times ((-8) - ((F(4))!)!) + (F((F(8) - 1)))) \\
 78483 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(8)) + 3)) \\
 78484 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(8)) + F(F(4)))) \\
 78494 &:= (F(7) \times ((-8!) + F(4!)) - (F(9) - 4!)) \\
 78495 &:= ((F(7) \times (-8!) + F(4!)) - (9 + 5!)) \\
 78496 &:= (-7!) - ((-8) \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - ((9!/6!)))) \\
 78507 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (-5) \times F((0! + F(7)))) \\
 78513 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((8!/5!) + 1)) - F(3!)) \\
 78520 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((8!/5!) + F(2))) - 0!) \\
 78521 &:= (F(F(7)) \times ((8!/5!) + (2 - 1))) \\
 78522 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((8!/5!) + F(2))) + F(2)) \\
 78523 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((8!/5!) + F(2))) + F(3)) \\
 78524 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times ((8!/5!) + F(2))) + F(4)) \\
 78533 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + (F((5 + F(3))) \times F(F(3!)))) \\
 78542 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (5! \times (-4^2))) \\
 78544 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (8!/5!)) + (4^4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78546 &:= (F(7) \times ((-(((8-5)!)+F(4!))-(F(6)!))) \\
 78554 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) - (F((5!/5)/(-4!))) \\
 78559 &:= (F(7) \times (-((8!+(5))) + F((-((5-9)!))) \\
 78584 &:= (-((7! - 8!)) + ((5! - F(F(8))) \times (-4))) \\
 78617 &:= (-((7! + 8!)) + (F((F(F(6)) + 1)) \times 7)) \\
 78622 &:= (((F(7)!)/((8! - 6!) \times 2)) - 2) \\
 78623 &:= (((F(7)!)/(8! - 6!)) - 2)/F(3) \\
 78624 &:= (((F(7) \times F(8)) \times (6 \times 2)) \times 4!) \\
 78625 &:= (((F(7) - 8) \times 6!) + F(25)) \\
 78628 &:= (((7 \times F(F(8))) - 6)/2) + 8! \\
 78633 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((8!/F((6 \times F(3))))^{F(3)})) \\
 78634 &:= (((7 \times F(F(8))) + 6)/F(3)) + (F((F(4)!))!) \\
 78636 &:= ((F((F(7) + 8)) + (6! \times 3)) \times 6) \\
 78637 &:= (((F(7)!)/((8! - 6!) \times F(3))) + F(7)) \\
 78643 &:= (7 - ((F(F(8)) + ((6! \times F(4)))) \times (-3!))) \\
 78644 &:= ((F(7) + ((F(F(8)) \times F(F(6)))/F(4)!)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 78653 &:= (-F(7) - ((-8!) + F((F(F(6)) - 5))) \times F(3)) \\
 78656 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-8)) + (F(6)!)) - 5!) + (F(6)!) \\
 78694 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(6) \times F(9)) + 4!))) \\
 78695 &:= (-F(F(7))) - (-8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (9 \times 5!))) \\
 78715 &:= (F(7) \times (-((8! - 7))) + F((-((1 - 5)!))) \\
 78724 &:= (((7 \times F(8)) \times F((F(7) + 2))) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\
 78733 &:= (((-7) + F(F(8))) \times 7) + (3 \times 3!!) \\
 78734 &:= (((7! \times 8) - F(F(7))) - 3!!) \times F(F(4)) \\
 78736 &:= (((-7 + F(8))^{7-3}) + (F(6)!)) \\
 78743 &:= ((7 + ((F(8) - 7)^4)) + (F(3)!)) \\
 78744 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(8)) + (7!)) \times F((F(4)!)) - ((F(4)!))!) \\
 78745 &:= (((7! + F(F(8))) - F(F(7))) - 4) \times 5) \\
 78748 &:= ((7 \times (F(F(8)) - (7!/4))) + F(F(8))) \\
 78749 &:= ((F(7) \times (-((8! - 7))) + F(4!)) + F(9)) \\
 78754 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (((-F(8)) + F(F(7))) + 5!) + (F(4)!)) \\
 78762 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-8)) - ((7 - (F(6)!)) \times 2)) \\
 78763 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times (-8)) - F(7)) - ((F(6)! \times (-F(3)))) \\
 78765 &:= (((7! + F(F(8))) - (F((7 + 6)))) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78769 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(F(8)/7)}) + (6! \times F(9))) \\
 78774 &:= (- (7!) + ((- (8!) + (F(F(7)) \times F(F(7)))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 78776 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-8)) + ((7! + 7!) \times F(6))) \\
 78783 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-8)) - (- (7) - (8! \times F(3)))) \\
 78817 &:= (((F(7))! / (8! + 8!)) + F(17)) \\
 78857 &:= (((((F(F(7)) \times (-8!)) - 8!) / (-5!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 78858 &:= (F(7) \times (F(F(8)) - (8 \times F((5!/8)))) \\
 78864 &:= (((((7! - F(8)) \times 8) - 6!) \times F(F(4))) \\
 78897 &:= (F(7) \times ((F(8) - 8!) + F(((- (9) + F(7)))))) \\
 78949 &:= (F(7) \times ((- ((8! + 9)) + F(4!)) + F(9))) \\
 78953 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((9 - 5!) \times (-3))) \\
 78967 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (8! - (9 \times (6! - 7!)))) \\
 78973 &:= ((F(7) - 8!) + ((9! - 7!) / 3)) \\
 78974 &:= (7 \times (F(F(8)) + ((9 + 7) \times F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 78976 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (8^{F(-9+F(7))})) - (F(6)!)) \\
 78985 &:= (((7! + F(F(8))) - (9 \times F(8))) \times 5) \\
 79024 &:= (7! + ((F(9) \times F((0! + 2)!))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 79043 &:= (- (F(((7 + 9) + 0!))) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(3)!)) \\
 79064 &:= ((- (7!) + ((9 - 0!)!) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 4)) \\
 79135 &:= (F(((F(7) - 9)!)) - (1 - (F(3!)^5))) \\
 79142 &:= (7 \times (F(F((9 - 1))) - (((F(4))!)/(-2)))) \\
 79185 &:= ((7! \times 9) - (F((-1 + F(8))) \times (-5))) \\
 79204 &:= (((((F(F(7)) - F(9))^2) + 0!) \times F(F(4))) \\
 79206 &:= (F(((F(7) - 9)!)) + ((2 + 0!) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 79216 &:= ((7! - F((9 + 2))) \times 16) \\
 79223 &:= (((((F(F(7)) - F(9))^2) \times 2) + F(F(3!))) \\
 79244 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) \times (2 + F((F(4)!))) + (4!)) \\
 79248 &:= ((7! + (- ((F(9) + 2)) \times F(4!))) / (-F(8))) \\
 79263 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times (-9)) + ((2 \times (F(6)!)) + 3!)) \\
 79296 &:= (((F(7) - 9)! \times (F((2 \times 9)) + 6!)) \\
 79317 &:= (((F(7) \times 9) \times (3!! + 1)) - (7!)) \\
 79324 &:= (7 \times ((9! / 32) - F((F(4)!))) \\
 79326 &:= ((F(7) \times 9) \times (3!! - (2 \times F(F(6)))) \\
 79335 &:= (((((7! + 9) \times 3) + 3!!) \times 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 79344 := $((7! - (9^{F(3)})) \times (4 \times 4))$
 79345 := $(7 \times (((-9!)/F(3!))/(-4) - (5)))$
 79346 := $((-7!) - ((-F(9)) \times 3!) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))$
 79347 := $((F(7) \times 9) \times 3!) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(F(7))))$
 79354 := $((7! + 9) - 3!) + F((5^{F(F(4))}))$
 79365 := $((F(7) \times 9) - 3!) \times (6! - (5))$
 79374 := $(7! + ((F(9) \times (3^7)) - 4!))$
 79376 := $((7! - F(9)) \times (3 + F(7))) - 6!$
 79378 := $((-((F(7) - (F(9)^3))) - F(F(7))) + 8!)$
 79380 := $((7 \times 9)^{F(3)} \times (F(8) - 0!))$
 79383 := $-(((F(F(7)) - ((F(9)^3) + 8!)) + F(3!)))$
 79391 := $-((F(F(7)) - (((F(9)^3) + ((9 - 1)!))))$
 79394 := $(7 \times (-((9!/(F(3) - F(9)))) + F(F(4))))$
 79424 := $(((((F(7))! + 9!)/(F((F(4)!))!)) - (F((F(2) + 4!))))$
 79433 := $(F(F(7)) - ((F((F(9) - 4!)) \times 3!) \times (-F(3))))$
 79434 := $(((-7) + F((-9) + 4!)) - (F(3)!)) \times (-F(F(4)))$
 79436 := $(7 \times ((9!/4)/F(3!)) + F(6))$
 79438 := $((7 \times F(9)) - (F(F(4)) \times (3! - 8!)))$
 79442 := $((F(F(7)) + 9) - (((F((F(4)!))! - ((F(4)!))!) \times (-2)))$
 79443 := $((7 - F((F(9) - (F(4)!))))/(-4) - F(3!))$
 79444 := $((((-7) \times F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \times F(F(4))) - (((F(4)!))!)$
 79446 := $-(((F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times (F(4)!)) - (F(F(4)) \times (F(6)!)))$
 79448 := $((F(F(7)) + 9) + F(4!)) + (F(4) \times F(F(8)))$
 79451 := $((7 - F((F(9) - (F(4)!))))/(-5 - 1))$
 79453 := $(F(F(7)) \times ((9 \times 4!) + (5^3)))$
 79454 := $((F(((F(7) - 9) + 4!)) + (5))/4)$
 79455 := $((7! - F((-9) + 4!)) + F((5 \times 5)))$
 79464 := $((F(7) + 9) \times ((F(4!) + (F(6)!))/4!))$
 79474 := $((F(F(7)) \times ((F(9) - F((F(4)!)) \times F(7))) + ((F(4)!))!)$
 79475 := $(7! - ((-((9!/4!)) + F(F(7))) \times 5))$
 79476 := $((F((-7) + F(9))) - (F((F(4)!))!)) + (-7 \times F(F(F(6))))$
 79483 := $((-F(7)) \times F((9 + F(F(4)))) + ((8! \times F(3))))$
 79485 := $((7! - F((9 + F(F(4)))) + F(F(8))) \times 5)$
 79486 := $((F(F(7)) \times (-F(9))) + F(4!)) + ((8! + 6!))$

- 79488 := ((7! + (F(9) × F((4 + 8)))) × 8)
- 79524 := (((F(7) + F(9)) × ((5 - 2)!)^{F(F(4))})
- 79533 := ((-((F((7 + 9)) + 5!)) + (F(3!)!) + (F(3!)!))
- 79534 := (((7! × 9) - 5!) × F(3)) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))
- 79536 := ((7! - (9! / (-5))) + ((F(3!)! / F(F(6))))
- 79547 := (((7! + (9 × 5!)) - F(F(F(4)))) × F(7))
- 79560 := ((F(7) × F(9)) × (5! + (60)))
- 79562 := ((-7) × (F(9) + 5!)) - ((F(6)!) × (-2))
- 79567 := (((7! × (-95)) / (-6)) - F(F(7)))
- 79573 := (F(7) × (((9 × 5!) + 7!) + F(F(3))))
- 79598 := (((F(7) × 9!) / 5!) - F(9)) + 8!
- 79624 := ((F((F((F(7) - 9)!)!))! + ((F((F(6) + F(2)))^{F(4)})))
- 79632 := (((7! - 9!) - (F(6)!) / (-3 + 2))
- 79634 := ((7! + ((9! + (6)) / 3)) - F(4!))
- 79635 := ((-F((F(7) + 9))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (3! × (-5!))
- 79638 := (-((F(7) × F((9 + 6)))) + (F(3!) × F(F(8))))
- 79641 := (((F(F(7)) × (-9)) + F(F(F(6)))) × (F((F(4)!) + 1))
- 79642 := ((F(7) × F(9)) - (((F(6)!) - ((F(4)!)!) × (-2)))
- 79643 := ((F(F(7)) × (-F(9))) + ((F(F(F(6))) × F((F(4)!) - 3))
- 79644 := ((-7!) - F((9 + F(6)))) × (-4 × F(4))
- 79645 := (F(7) + ((9 - 6!) × (F((F(4)!) - 5!)))
- 79646 := (7 × (((9 × F(6)) × (F(4)!) + F(F(F(6))))
- 79653 := ((-F((7 + 9))) + (F(6)!) + ((5 + 3)!))
- 79658 := (((F(7) × F(9)) × F((6 + 5))) + 8!)
- 79664 := (((-F((7 + 9))) + F(F(F(6)))) × F(6)) - F((F(4)!)
- 79674 := (-((7! - 9!)) + (6 × (7 - F(4!))))
- 79682 := (((-7) × F(9)) - 6!) - (8! × (-2))
- 79684 := ((F(F(7)) + ((9 - 6!) + 8!)) × F(F(4)))
- 79687 := -((F(F(7)) - ((9! - 6!) + (8! × (-7))))
- 79723 := (7 × (((F(9) × F(7)) + F(2)) + F(F(F(3!))))
- 79732 := (-((F(7) × F(9))) - ((F(F(7)) - (F(3!)!) × 2))
- 79734 := (7! + ((F(9) × (F(7)³)) - (4)))
- 79735 := (-F(F(7))) - (((F(9) × (-7)) × (F(3!)!) / 5!))
- 79736 := (((7! + F(9)) + (F(F(7)) × F(F(3!)))) × F(6))

- 79742** := (((-7) - (F(9) × F(7))) + (F((F(4)!)))! × 2)
79743 := (-F(7) + ((-((F(9) × F(7))) + (F((F(4)!)))! × F(3)))
79746 := (7! + ((F(9) × (F(7)^{F(4)})) + F(6)))
79748 := (((7! × 9) - F(7)) × F(F(4))) - F(F(8)))
79763 := (7 - (((F(9) × F(7)) - (F(6)!)) × F(3)))
79768 := (F(7) × (((F(9) + F(7)) + 6!) × 8))
79782 := (((F(7) × F(9)) - F(7)) - 8!) × (-2))
79787 := (((F(7)!)/(9!/7)) - (8! + F(7)))
79793 := (((((F(7)! - 9!) × (-7))/(-9!)) - (F(3)!))!
79805 := (7! + (((-9!) - F(F(8))) + 0!)/(-5))
79824 := (((7! - F(9)) × ((8/2)!)) - (F((F(4)!)))!
79826 := (((F(7) + F(9)) - 8!) × (-2)) - 6!
79838 := (-(((7! × F(9)) - (8^{3!}))) - F(F(8)))
79842 := (-798 - ((F((F(4)!)))! × (-2)))
79844 := (((F(F(7)) - F(9)) - (8!/F(F(4)))) × (-4))
79845 := (((7! - 9) + F(F(8))) - F((F(4)!)) × 5)
79847 := ((7!/(-9)) - ((-8!) × F(F(4))) + F(F(7)))
79848 := (((7! - 9) × 8) - ((F(4)!))! + 8!)
79855 := (((-((7! + 9)) - F(F(8))) × (-5)) - 5!)
79856 := (F(((F(7) - 9)!)) - (-((8⁵)) - 6!))
79863 := -((F(F(7)) + (((F(9) × 8) - (F(6)!)) × F(3))))
79865 := (((7! - F(9)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) × 5)
79873 := -((F(F(7)) + (((F(9) - 8!) + F(F(7))) × F(3))))
79885 := (((7! - (9!/8!)) + F(F(8))) × 5)
79886 := (-((7 - 9) × (8! - F((8 + 6))))
79924 := (((F((7 + 9)) × F(9)) - 2) + F(4!))
79933 := ((F(7) + ((9!/9) × F(3))) - 3!!)
79935 := (((-((7! + (9/9))) - F(F(F(3!)))) × (-5))
79936 := (((7! + 9) × 9) × F(3)) - F(F(F(6))))
79937 := ((7! + F((F(9) - 9))) - (F(3)⁷))
79945 := ((7! + F((F(9) - 9))) + (4! × (-5)))
79946 := (((F(7) - (9!/(-9))) × F(F(4))) - (6!))
79953 := (((7! + F((F(9) - 9))) - 5!) + F(3!))
79954 := (7 × ((F(9) × (9 + 5)) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))))
79975 := (((-((7! + 9)) - F((F(9) - F(7)))) × (-5))

- 79984** := $((7! - ((9 \times 9))) + F((F(8) + (4))))$
79993 := $((7! + F((F(9) - 9))) - (9 \times F(3!)))$
79994 := $((F(7) \times F((9 + 9))) + F(9)) + F(4!))$
80044 := $((((8 - 0!))! + F((0! + 4!))) - F(F((F(4)!)))$
80057 := $((- (8) + F((0! + (-((0! - (5))))!))) + (7!))$
80064 := $((((8 - 0!))! - 0!) + F((F(F(6)) + 4)))$
80065 := $(((8 - 0!))! + F(((0! - (6)) \times (-5))))$
80172 := $(((8! - 0!) - F(F((1 \times 7)))) \times 2)$
80174 := $((8! - F(F(((0 \times 1) + 7)))) \times F(F(4)))$
80263 := $((8! \times 02) - F((F(6) + 3!)))$
80327 := $((- (80) - (((F(3!))! \times (-2)) + F(F(7))))$
80339 := $((- (F(F((8 - 0!))) + (- (F(3)) \times ((F(3!))! - F(9))))$
80344 := $(8! + ((F((0! + F(3!)))^{F(4)} + ((F(4)!))!))$
80346 := $((F((F(8) + 0!)) - (3!! \times (F(4)!)) \times 6)$
80352 := $((8! - F(((0! + 3!) + (5)))) \times 2)$
80353 := $((- (8!) - ((03)!)) + F((5 + F(F(3!))))$
80354 := $(((8! + 0!) - (3!!/5)) \times F(F(4)))$
80367 := $((8! \times F(03)) - (F(F(6)) \times F(7)))$
80368 := $(((((F((8 + 0!)) \times F(3!)) - (F(6)!)) - 8!))$
80369 := $(((8! + 0!) + (F(3!))! - ((F(6) \times F(9))))$
80373 := $(((8! - F((0! + F(3!)))) - F(F(7))) + (F(3)!))$
80374 := $(((8! - (-((0! - 3!)))! - F(7)) \times F(F(4)))$
80383 := $(((8! - 0!) - (F(3)^8)) + (F(3)!))$
80384 := $(((8! - (-((0! - 3!)))! - 8) \times F(F(4)))$
80386 := $((8! - F(F((0! + 3!)))) - (- (8!) + F(F(6))))$
80387 := $((- (((F(8) - 0!) - (F(3) \times 8!)) - F(F(7)))$
80389 := $((- (F(F((8 - 0!))) - ((F(3) \times (8! - 9))))$
80397 := $(((8! - 0!) + (F(3!))! - (9 + F(F(7))))$
80398 := $((8! - F(F((0! + 3!)))) - (9 - 8!))$
80406 := $(((8! - 0!) + (F((F(4)!))!)) - (F(F((0! + (6))))))$
80407 := $((- ((8! \times (0! - F(4)))) - F(F(07)))$
80408 := $(((8! + 0!) + (F((F(4)!))!)) - F(F(-((0! - 8))))$
80408 := $(((8! + 0!) + (F((F(4)!))!)) - F(F(-((0! - 8))))$
80427 := $((F(8) - 0!) - (((F((F(4)!))! \times (-2)) + F(F(7))))$
80428 := $((F(8) - F(F((0! + (F(4)!)))) - (- (2) \times 8!))$

$$\begin{aligned}80432 &:= (((-80) - 4!) + (F(3)!)) \times 2 \\80436 &:= -(((F((8 + 0!)) \times (F(4)!)) + (-F(3) \times (F(6)!))) \\80442 &:= (((8! - ((0! + (4))))!) + F(F((F(4)!))) \times 2 \\80446 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times F(F(4))) - (4! \times F(6))) \\80447 &:= ((8! - 0!) + (F((F(4)!)) \times (-4! - 7!))) \\80449 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times F(F(4))) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times 9)) \\80462 &:= ((8! - F((0! + (4 + 6)))) \times 2 \\80464 &:= (((8! + 0!) - F((F(4) + F(6)))) \times F(F(4))) \\80472 &:= (((8! + 0!) + (F((F(4)!))!) - (F(7)^2)) \\80473 &:= (((8! + 0!) \times F(F(4))) - ((F(7)^{F(3)})) \\80474 &:= (((8! + 0!) \times F(F(4))) - (7 \times 4!)) \\80475 &:= (-F((F(8) - 0!)) - (((F(4)!))! + 7) \times (-5!)) \\80482 &:= (((80 - F(F(F(4)))) - 8!) \times (-2)) \\80484 &:= (((-80) + F(F(4))) + 8!) \times F(F(4)) \\80487 &:= (80 - ((F(F(4)) \times (-8!)) + F(F(7)))) \\80492 &:= (-80 - (((F((F(4)!))!) - F(9)) \times (-2)) \\80494 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times F(F(4))) - F((9 + F(4)))) \\80495 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 0!) + (F(4!)/9)) \times 5) \\80496 &:= ((8! - F((F(04) + 9))) + (F(6)!)) \\80497 &:= (F(((F(8) - 0!) + F(4))) - (9!/(-7))) \\80498 &:= (((8! + 0!) \times F(F(4))) - F((-9) + F(8))) \\80520 &:= ((8! - (05!)) + (F((2 + 0!))!)) \\80521 &:= (((8! + 0!) - 5!) + (F((2 + 1)!))!)) \\80523 &:= (((8! + 0!) - 5!) + 2) + (F(3)!)) \\80533 &:= (((F((8 - 0!)) - 5!) + (F(3)!))! + (F(3)!)) \\80534 &:= ((8! + (0 - 53)) \times F(F(4))) \\80535 &:= ((8! + (F((0! + (5))))!) - (F(F(3!)) \times 5)) \\80536 &:= ((8! + 0!) + ((-5) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(6)!)) \\80542 &:= (((F(8) + 0!) - 5!) - ((F((F(4)!))!) \times (-2)) \\80543 &:= (((8! - 0!) - 5!) + 4!) + (F(3)!)) \\80544 &:= ((8! - (F((0! + (5)))) \times (F(4)!)) \times F(F(4))) \\80562 &:= (((8! + 0!) - (5 \times F(6))) \times 2) \\80570 &:= ((8! + (F((0! + (5))))!) - (70)) \\80574 &:= (((8! - 0!) + (-5) \times F(7)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) \\80575 &:= ((8! + (F((0! + (5))))!) - (F(7) \times 5))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 80576 &:= (((8! + 0!) + (-5) \times F(7)) + (F(6))!) \\
 80582 &:= (((8! - F((0! + 5)))) - (F(8))) \times 2 \\
 80583 &:= (((8! + 0!) - (58)) + (F(3))!) \\
 80584 &:= ((-8!)/((0! + 5)))! - (-8!) \times F(F(4))) \\
 80593 &:= (F(8) + ((F((0! + 5))))! - F(9)) \times F(3)) \\
 80594 &:= (((8! + 0!) - (-((5 - 9)))! \times F(F(4))) \\
 80595 &:= ((8! + (F((0! + 5))))! - (9 \times 5)) \\
 80596 &:= (((8! + 0!) - (5 \times 9)) + (F(6))!) \\
 80598 &:= ((8! - F((0! + 5)))) - (F(9) - 8!) \\
 80600 &:= (((F(8) - 0!) - (F(6))!) \times (-0! + 0!)) \\
 80602 &:= (((F(8) - 0!) - (F(6))!) - 0!) \times (-2) \\
 80604 &:= -((F((8 + 0!)) - ((F(6))! - 0!) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 80606 &:= ((8! + (F(06))!) - F((0! + F(6)))) \\
 80612 &:= (((8! - 0!) - F((6 + 1))) \times 2) \\
 80614 &:= ((-8!) + F((0! + (6)))) \times (1 - F(4)) \\
 80615 &:= (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) - (-((1 - 5)))!) \\
 80616 &:= ((8! - (-((0! - (6 - 1))))!) + (F(6))!) \\
 80618 &:= ((-((F(8) + 0!)) + (F(6))!) + ((1 \times 8))!) \\
 80619 &:= ((8! + (F(06))!) - F(-((1 - 9)))) \\
 80620 &:= ((8! + (F(06))!) - (20)) \\
 80621 &:= (((8! - 0!) - F(6)) \times 2) - 1) \\
 80622 &:= (((8! - F(06)) \times 2) - 2) \\
 80623 &:= (((8! + 0!) - F(6)) \times 2) - 3) \\
 80624 &:= ((8! - F(06)) \times (-2 - 4)) \\
 80626 &:= (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) - F((F(2) + (6)))) \\
 80627 &:= ((8! \times ((0 \times 6) + 2)) - F(7)) \\
 80629 &:= (((8! - 0!) \times F((6/2))) - 9) \\
 \\
 80630 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 0 \\
 80631 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 1 \\
 80632 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 2 \\
 80633 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 3 \\
 80634 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 4 \\
 80635 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 5 \\
 80636 &:= (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$80637 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 7$$

$$80638 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 8$$

$$80639 := (8! + 0! - 6) \times F(3) + 9$$

$$80640 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 0$$

$$80641 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 1$$

$$80642 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 2$$

$$80643 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 3$$

$$80644 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 4$$

$$80645 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 5$$

$$80646 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 6$$

$$80647 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 7$$

$$80648 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 8$$

$$80649 := 8! \times (06 - 4) + 9$$

$$80650 := (((8! - 0!) + (6)) \times F(F((5 - 0!))))$$

$$80652 := ((8! + 06) \times F((5 - 2)))$$

$$80653 := ((8! + (F(06))!) + F((5 + F(3))))$$

$$80654 := (((8! + 0!) + (6)) \times (5 - F(4)))$$

$$80656 := (((8! + 0!) + (F(6))!) + (5!/F(6)))$$

$$80657 := (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) + (5 + F(7)))$$

$$80658 := (((8! + 0!) + F(6)) \times F(-((5 - 8))))$$

$$80659 := (F(8) - ((0! - (F(6))!) \times F(F(-((5 - 9))))))$$

$$80660 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 0$$

$$80661 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 1$$

$$80662 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 2$$

$$80663 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 3$$

$$80664 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 4$$

$$80665 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 5$$

$$80666 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 6$$

$$80667 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 7$$

$$80668 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 8$$

$$80669 := 8! - 0! + F(6)! + F(F(6)) + 9$$

$$80672 := (((((8! + 0!) + F(6)) + (7)) \times 2)$$

- 80673** := (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) + F((7 + F(3))))
80674 := ((- (8!) + F((0! + F(6)))) + (7! × 4!))
80675 := ((8! + (F(06))!) + (7 × 5))
80682 := ((8! + F(((0 × 6) + 8))) × 2)
80683 := (((F(8) + 0!) + F(F(6))) + ((8! × F(3))))
80684 := (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) + (F(8) + 4!))
80687 := ((8! + F((0! + F(6)))) + (8! + F(7)))
80692 := (((8! - F(06)) + F(9)) × 2)
80693 := (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) + (9 × 3!))
80694 := (((8! - 0!) + (F(6))!) + F((F(9) - 4!)))
80696 := (((8! + 0!) + F(F(6))) + F(9)) + (F(6))!
80724 := ((8! + (F((0! + (7))) × 2)) × F(F(4)))
80728 := (((8! - 0!) + F((F(7) - 2))) + 8!)
80729 := ((8! + ((0! + (7)))!) + (F((2 + 9))))
80733 := (((80 + F(7)) + (F(3!))!) + (F(3!))!)
80734 := (((F((8 + 0!)) + F(7)) + (F(3!))!) × F(F(4)))
80736 := (8! + ((-((0! - F(7))) × F(3!)) + (F(6))!))
80742 := (((8! - 0!) + (F(7) × 4)) × 2)
80743 := ((8! - 0!) + ((F(7) × F((F(4))!)) + (F(3!))!))
80744 := ((8! + (F(07) × 4)) × F(F(4)))
80745 := ((8! + ((0! + (7)))!) + (F(F((F(4))!)) × 5))
80753 := (((8! - 07) + 5!) + (F(3!))!)
80754 := (((8! + ((0! + (7)))!) + 5!) - (F(4))!)
80760 := ((8! + ((0! + (7)))!) + ((6 - 0!))!)
80763 := ((- (F(8)) + F(-((0! - F(7)))))) - ((F(6))! × (-F(3)))
80766 := ((-((F(8) × (0! - (7)))) + (F(6))!) + (F(6))!)
80768 := ((8 + (07)!) × (F(6) + 8))
80782 := ((8! + F(-((0! - F(7)))))) + ((8! - 2))
80783 := ((8! + F(-((0! - F(7)))))) - (- (8!) + F(F(3)))
80784 := (((- (8) - 0!) - 7!) × (8 - 4!))
80786 := (((8! - 0!) + (7 × F(8))) + (F(6))!)
80787 := ((8! + ((0! + (7)))!) + (F(8) × 7))
80788 := ((8! + 0!) - ((- (7) × F(8)) - 8!))
80793 := (((8! + F(-((0! - F(7)))))) + 9) + (F(3!))!)
80796 := (-((F((F(8) + 0!)) + 7)) + (9 × F(F(F(6))))))

- 80803** := $-((F((F(8) - 0!)) + ((F(F(8)) \times (-0!)) \times F(3!))))$
- 80839** := $(F(F((8 - 0!))) + (((8! \times F(3)) - F(9))))$
- 80842** := $((80 + F(8)) + (F((F(4))!))! \times 2)$
- 80844** := $((F((8 + 0!)) + (8!/F(4))) \times (F(4))!)$
- 80847** := $-((((F((8 - 0!)) - 8!) \times F(F(4))) - F(F(7))))$
- 80848** := $(8 \times (((-(0! - 8))!)/(-(F(4))!) + F(F(8))))$
- 80852** := $((8! + 0!) - (F(8) \times (-5))) \times 2)$
- 80854** := $-(((F((8 - 0!)) - (8! + 5!)) \times F(F(4))))$
- 80856** := $(8 \times ((0! + F(F(8))) - (5! + 6!)))$
- 80867** := $((8! + (08)!) - (6)) + F(F(7))$
- 80871** := $((8! - 0!) + 8!) + F(F(7)) - 1$
- 80872** := $((8! - 0!) + 8!) + F((F(7) \times F(2)))$
- 80873** := $((8! + (08)!) + F((7 + 3!)))$
- 80874** := $((8! + ((0! + 8) \times F(7))) \times F(F(4)))$
- 80878** := $(8! + ((F((0! + 8)) \times 7) + 8!))$
- 80879** := $((8! + 0!) + 8!) - (-7 \times F(9))$
- 80946** := $((8 + 0!) \times F(9)) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(6))!)$
- 80947** := $((F((F(8) - 0!)) \times (9 + F(4))) - F(F(7)))$
- 80953** := $((F((-8) + F(09))) - 5!) - (F(3))!)$
- 80964** := $((F((F(8) - 0!)) + 9) \times 6) + (F((F(4))!))!)$
- 80976** := $((8 - 0!) + 9) \times (7! + F(F(6)))$
- 81017** := $((8! \times (1 + 0!)) + F((1 + F(7))))$
- 81072** := $(-(8! + 1)) + F((F(07) \times 2))$
- 81073** := $(-(8!)) + F(((1 + 0!) + ((7 - 3))!))$
- 81074** := $(-(8! - 1)) + F((F(07) \times F(F(4))))$
- 81144** := $((-(8 - 1)) \times F(((1 \times 4)!) / (-4))$
- 81174** := $((F((F(8) - 1)) \times (-1 + F(7))) - (F(4))!)$
- 81180** := $((F((8 - 1)) - 1) \times F((F(8) - 0!)))$
- 81248** := $((8! - 1) \times 2) + F(-(((F(4))! - (F(8))))))$
- 81264** := $((8 + 1)! / (-2)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 4!)$
- 81275** := $(8! + ((-1 + (2^{F(7)})) \times 5))$
- 81326** := $((-F((8 + 1))) + 3!) + (2 \times (F(6))!)$
- 81334** := $((8! - 1) \times F(3)) + 3! - (4!)$
- 81336** := $((8! - ((1 + 3))! + 3!) + (F(6))!)$
- 81337** := $((8! - 1) \times F(3)) + (3 \times F(F(7)))$

$$\begin{aligned}81338 &:= ((-(F(8) + 1)) + 3!) + ((F(3) \times 8!)) \\81344 &:= (((8! - F(((1 \times 3)!)) \times F(F(4))) + ((F(4))!)) \\81346 &:= (((8! - 1) - 3!) \times F(F(4))) + (6!)) \\81347 &:= (((8! \times F((1 \times 3))) + ((F(4))!)) - F(7)) \\81349 &:= (((8! - 1) \times F(3)) + ((F(4))!)) - 9) \\81353 &:= (((8! - 1) \times F(3)) - (5)) + 3!!) \\81354 &:= (-(((8 - 1)!)) - ((3!! \times (-5!)) + (F(4)!)) \\81356 &:= (((8! + 1) + 3!) - (5)) + (F(6)!)) \\81358 &:= (((8! - 1) \times F(3)) + ((-(5 - 8))!)) \\81359 &:= (((8! - 1) + (F(3)!)) + ((F(-(5 - 9))))!)) \\ \\81360 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 0 \\81361 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 1 \\81362 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 2 \\81363 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 3 \\81364 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 4 \\81365 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 5 \\81366 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 6 \\81367 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 7 \\81368 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 8 \\81369 &:= 8! \times F(1 \times 3) + 6! + 9 \\ \\81373 &:= (((8! \times F((1 \times 3))) + F(7)) + 3!!) \\81374 &:= (((8! + 1) + (F(3)!)) + F(7)) + ((F(4))!)) \\81375 &:= (F(8) \times (((1 + 3)!)) - (F(F(7)) \times 5)) \\81382 &:= (((F(8) + 1) + 3!) - (8! \times (-2))) \\81383 &:= (((8! + 1) \times F(3)) + F(8)) + 3!!) \\81384 &:= ((8! + (((1 \times 3)!)) + ((8! + 4!)) \\81393 &:= (((8! - 1) + (F(3)!)) + (F(9) + 3!)) \\81394 &:= ((8! + F((-1 + 3! + 9))) \times F(F(4))) \\81396 &:= (((8! + 1) \times F(3)) + F(9)) + 6! \\81432 &:= ((-(F((F(8) - 1))) - F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (3! \times (-2))) \\81442 &:= (((8! + F(14)) + 4!) \times 2) \\81482 &:= ((F(F(8))/F((1 + (F(4)!)))) - (8! \times (-2))) \\81522 &:= ((8! + (F(F((1 + 5)))^2)) \times 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}81536 &:= ((-8) + ((1 \times 5)!) \times (F(3!) + (6!))) \\81568 &:= (-(((8-1)!) - ((-5!) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8))) \\81572 &:= ((8! + (F(F(-(1-5)))) \times F(F(7)))) \times 2) \\81594 &:= (((F(8) - 1) \times 5!) \times F(9)) - (F(4)!) \\81595 &:= (((F(8) - 1) \times 5!) \times F(9)) - (5)) \\81626 &:= (((8! - 1) + (F(6)!) + F((2 \times F(6)))) \\81627 &:= ((8! + F(16)) + ((F(2) + (7))))! \\81628 &:= (((8! + F(16)) + F(2)) + 8!) \\81633 &:= (((8! + F(16)) + 3!) + (F(3)!))! \\81641 &:= ((8-1) \times ((F(6)!) - F((4-1)))) \\81644 &:= (((8! - ((1+6)!) - (4)) + F(4!)) \\81647 &:= (((8! - 1) + F((6 \times 4))) - 7!) \\81648 &:= -((((8-1)!) - F((6 \times 4))) - 8!) \\81657 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (1+6)) + (-5) + 7!) \\81661 &:= (((8-1) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (6!))) - 1) \\81662 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (-1 \times 6!)) \times (F(6) - F(2))) \\81663 &:= (((8-1) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (6!))) + F(F(3))) \\81664 &:= (8! - (-16) \times F((-6) + 4!)) \\81670 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (-1 - 6!)) \times 7) + 0!) \\81676 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (1 - 6!)) \times 7) + F(F(6))) \\81677 &:= (8 + (((1 + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7) + (7!))) \\81683 &:= ((8-1) \times ((6! + F(F(8))) + 3)) \\81738 &:= (-((8+1) \times ((F(F(7)) \times F(3!)) - F(F(8)))) \\81743 &:= (81 + (7 \times (((F(4)!)! + F(F(F(3)))))) \\81744 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (1+7)) - ((F(4)!)!) \times F((F(4)!)) \\81775 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 1) \times 7) + (7! + 5!)) \\81783 &:= (F(F((8-1))) \times (F(7) \times (F(8) + 3!))) \\81784 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (-((1-7)!) \times 8) - (4!)) \\81790 &:= (F((F(8) - 1)) + F((((F(7) - 9)!) + 0!))) \\81792 &:= (-F(F(8)) - ((-1 - F(((F(7) - 9)!) \times 2)) \\81793 &:= (-((8! - F((17+9)))) + 3!!) \\81808 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((-((1-8) - 0!))!) \times 8) \\81816 &:= (8 \times (F(F((1 \times 8))) + (1 - 6!))) \\81824 &:= ((F((8+1)) - F(F(8))) - (-2) \times F(4!)) \\81826 &:= (((F(F((8-1))) + 8!) \times 2) + (6!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}81832 &:= (8 \times (((1 + F(F(8))) - 3!) + 2)) \\81837 &:= (-(F(8)) \times (-1 + (-8) \times (3! - F(F(7))))) \\81856 &:= (8 \times ((1 + F(F(8))) + (5 - 6!))) \\81862 &:= (((8! + 1) + F((F(8) - (6)))) \times 2) \\81864 &:= (8 \times (((1 + F(F(8))) - (6!)) + (F(4)!)) \\82037 &:= (((8! \times 2) - 0!) - (-3!) \times F(F(7))) \\82064 &:= (((-8!) + F((2 + 0!))) - (6!)) \times (-F(F(4))) \\82095 &:= ((F(F(8))/(-2)) \times (-0! + (9 + 5))) \\82237 &:= ((8! \times 2) + F((F(2) + 3) + F(7))) \\82239 &:= (((8! + F(2)) \times 2) + F((F(3!) + 9))) \\82284 &:= ((822 + 8!) \times F(F(4))) \\82328 &:= ((F(F(8))/(-2)) - (F(F(3!)) \times (-F((-2) + F(8)))) \\82328 &:= ((F(F(8))/(-2)) - (F(F(3!)) \times (-F((-2) + F(8)))) \\82335 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(2))) + 3!) \times (3! + (5))) \\82344 &:= (((F((F(8) - 2)) - 3!) \times 4!) - ((F(4)!)) \\82347 &:= (((8! \times 2) + 3!) + F((F(4) + F(7)))) \\82362 &:= -((F(F(8)) - (2 \times ((3!^6) - 2))) \\82363 &:= -((F(F(8)) - ((2 \times (3!^6) - 3))) \\82364 &:= -(((F(F(8)) + (-2) \times (3!^6))) + F(F(4))) \\82365 &:= (F((F(8) - F(2))) - ((3! \times F(F(6))) \times (-5))) \\82368 &:= (F((8 - F(2))) \times ((3!^6) - 8!)) \\82372 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 2) - ((3! \times 7!) \times (-2))) \\82374 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(2) + (3! \times 7!)))) \times F(F(4))) \\82383 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - F(2)) - ((3! + F(F(8))) \times F(3!))) \\82384 &:= (-((F(F(8)) - 2)) - (-((3! + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)))) \\82393 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 2) + F(F(3!))) + (9!/3!)) \\82432 &:= ((-((8^2)) \times F(4!))/(-3!^2)) \\82455 &:= (((8 - 2)! - F(4)) \times (5! - (5))) \\82463 &:= ((8! \times 2) + ((F((F(4)!)) - F(F(F(6))))/(-3!))) \\82464 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 2)/F(4)!)) + ((F(6)! \times F(F(4)))) \\82486 &:= -((((F((F(8) - 2)) - F(4!)) - 8!) + F(F(6)))) \\82488 &:= ((8! \times 2) + (F(F((F(4)!)) \times 88)) \\82496 &:= (8 \times (((-2) \times F(4!))/(-9)) + F(6)) \\82498 &:= -(((F((F(8) - 2)) - F(4!)) + (9 - 8!))) \\82527 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(2) + (5)))) - (F(2) + 7!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 82528 &:= -((((8 - F(2)))! - (F(((5 - 2)))! \times F(F(8)))))) \\
 82528 &:= -((((8 - F(2)))! - (F(((5 - 2)))! \times F(F(8)))))) \\
 82533 &:= (-((((8 - F(2)))! - (5))) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-F(3!)))) \\
 82536 &:= ((8 - ((2 + 5)!)) + (F(3!) \times F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 82544 &:= ((- (8!) - (-((F(2) - 5!)) \times F((F(4)!)))) \times (-F(F(4)))) \\
 82547 &:= (F((F(8) - F(2))) - ((- (5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \times (-7))) \\
 82560 &:= ((8 \times 2) \times (5! + ((F(6) - 0!)!)) \\
 82562 &:= (((8! + F(2)) + (5! \times F(6))) \times 2) \\
 82563 &:= (-((F(8) + (-2) \times 5!)) \times F((F(6) + 3!))) \\
 82564 &:= (((8! + 2) + (5! \times F(6))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 82567 &:= (((F(8) + 2) \times 5) \times 6!) - F(F(7))) \\
 82568 &:= (8 + (2 \times ((5! \times F(6)) + 8!)) \\
 82612 &:= (((8! + F((2 \times F(6)))) - 1) \times 2) \\
 82614 &:= ((8! + F((2 \times F(6)))) \times (-1 + F(4))) \\
 82627 &:= (((8! + F((2 \times F(6)))) \times 2) + F(7)) \\
 82635 &:= (F(8) - (2 \times (-((F(6)!)) - F((F(F(3!)) - (5)))))) \\
 82644 &:= -(((((((8 - F(2)))! + 6) - F(4!)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 82647 &:= (- (F(8)) - (2 \times ((- (6) - F(4!)) + (7!)))) \\
 82649 &:= ((F((F(8) - 2)) \times F(F(6))) - (F(4!)/9)) \\
 82654 &:= (- (F(F(8))) + ((2 \times 65) \times ((F(4)!)!)) \\
 82656 &:= (- (82) \times ((- (6) - 5!) \times F(6))) \\
 82664 &:= (8 - (2 \times (((F(6)!)/F(6)) - F(4!)))) \\
 82672 &:= ((F(((8/2)!)) + ((F(6) - 7!))) \times 2) \\
 82677 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(2))) + (6 + 7!)) \times 7) \\
 82684 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((F(2) + (6)))!) \times (8 + (F(4)!)) \\
 82688 &:= (8! + (((2^{F(6)}) \times 8) + 8!)) \\
 82698 &:= ((8! \times 2) + (F(F(6)) \times 98)) \\
 82736 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((2 + F(7)))) + 3!) \times F(6)) \\
 82737 &:= ((8! \times 2) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(3) + (7)))) \\
 82764 &:= -((F(F(8)) + (2 \times ((F(F(7)) - (6!)) - F(4!)))) \\
 82768 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (-((2 - 7)!)) - (6!)) \times 8) \\
 82827 &:= ((8! \times 2) + (F((8/2))^7)) \\
 82845 &:= ((8! \times 2) + ((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) \times 5)) \\
 82846 &:= (((8! - 2) + 8!) + (F(4!)/F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}82847 &:= (((8! + F((2 \times 8))) \times F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \\82848 &:= (((F(8) \times 2) \times 8!) + F(4!))/F(8) \\82854 &:= (((8! + F((2 \times 8))) + 5!) \times F(F(4))) \\82863 &:= ((8! \times 2) + ((F(8) + 6!) \times 3)) \\82864 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (28 \times F(F(6)))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\82923 &:= (((8 \times (2 + F(9)))^2) - F(F(3!))) \\82937 &:= (((-8) + F(2)) + 9!) - (3!^7) \\82940 &:= ((F((F(8) - 2)) - F(9)) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!)) \\82946 &:= (F(F(8)) - ((2 - (F(9) \times F(4))) \times 6!)) \\82947 &:= ((F((8/2)) + 9!) - ((F(4))!^7)) \\82967 &:= (((F(8) + 2) + 9!) - (6^7)) \\83039 &:= -((((F(8) + F(3))^{0!+3}) - 9!)) \\83064 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(3))) + (0 - 6!)) \times 4!) \\83088 &:= ((-8!)/(F(3!) + 0!)) + (F(F(8)) \times 8) \\83089 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) + (0! - (8!/9))) \\83134 &:= (-F(F(8))) + (((F(3))! \times (-1 - 3!))/(-F(4))) \\83157 &:= ((-8) + ((3! + 1)!) + (5^7)) \\83193 &:= ((8! - F(3)) + ((1 + F(9))^3)) \\83194 &:= ((8! - F(F(3))) + (((1 + F(9))^{F(4)}))) \\83218 &:= (((8! - 3) \times 2) + F(18)) \\83223 &:= ((F((F(8) - 3)) - F(2)) - (-2 \times (F(3))!)) \\83224 &:= ((8! \times F(3)) + F((22 - 4))) \\83226 &:= ((F((F(8) - 3)) + 2) + (2 \times (F(6))!)) \\83228 &:= (F((F(8) - 3)) - (2 \times (-2 - 8!))) \\83234 &:= (F(F(8)) + (((3^2) \times 3!) + F(4!))) \\83236 &:= (((8! + 3!) \times 2) + F((3 \times 6))) \\83237 &:= (F((F(8) - 3)) - ((-2) \times (F(3))!) - F(7)) \\83244 &:= (-F(8)) \times ((F((F(3!) \times 2)) + 4) \times (-4)) \\83246 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - 2) + ((F(4))! \times (-6!))) \\83264 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 2)) - (6! \times (F(4))!)) \\83266 &:= (F((F(8) - 3)) + (2 \times ((F(6))! + F(F(6)))))) \\83296 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((3! \times F((2 + 9)))) \times F(6)) \\83317 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(3))) + 3!) \times 17) \\83319 &:= (-F(8)) - (((F(F(3!))³) - 1) \times (-9)) \\83323 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(3!)) \times F(3!)) - F((-2) + F(F(3!))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83331 &:= (((F(8)^3) - F(3)) \times (F(3!) + 1)) \\83334 &:= (((-8!) - F((F(3) \times F(3!)))) \times (-F(3))) + ((F(4))!) \\83336 &:= (-8) \times (((F(3) + F(F(3!)))^{F(3)} - F(F(F(6)))) \\83339 &:= (8 - (((F(F(3!))^3) - F(3)) \times (-9))) \\83340 &:= ((8 + F(F(3))) \times ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)} - 0!)) \\83341 &:= (-8) + ((F(F(3!))^3) \times (F((F(4))!) + 1)) \\83342 &:= ((8!/3!) + (F(F(F(3!))) \times ((F(4))! + F(2)))) \\83343 &:= (((F(8) \times 3)^3)/F(4) - 3!) \\83344 &:= (-8!) - (F(3!) \times ((-3!) - F(4!))/F(4)) \\83346 &:= ((F(8) + F(3!)) \times (-3! + (-4) \times 6!)) \\83347 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)} - 7!)) \\83358 &:= ((F(F(8))/F((F(F(3)) + 3!))) \times (5! - F(8))) \\83363 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 3) \times F(3!)) - F((F(F(6)) - F(3)))) \\83366 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - F((-F(3) + F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)))) \\83373 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) \times 3) + (7! \times 3!)) \\83374 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) + ((-3!) \times F(F(7))) \times F(4)) \\83376 &:= ((F((8 \times 3)) \times F(3)) - (F(7) \times 6!)) \\83377 &:= (((((8 \times 3)!)/(F(F(3!))!) - F(F(7))) \times 7) \\83379 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 3!) - F(3!)) + F((F(7) + 9))) \\83381 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) \times 3!) + F((F(8) + 1))) \\83384 &:= ((8! \times F(3)) + ((3! + 8)^{F(4)})) \\83385 &:= ((F((8 \times F(3))) - 3!) \times 85) \\83392 &:= ((-F(8)) \times 3!!) + ((F(F(F(3!))) \times 9) - 2) \\83393 &:= ((-F(8)) \times 3!!) + ((F(F(F(3!))) \times 9) - F(F(3))) \\83394 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (3 \times 3)) - ((9!/4!)) \\83396 &:= (((-F(8)) \times 3!!) + F(3)) + (9 \times F(F(F(6)))) \\83403 &:= (((F(8)^3) + (F(4))!) \times (0! + F(3!))) \\83404 &:= ((F(8) + F(3!)) \times (((F(4))!) - 0!) \times 4) \\83408 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 3!) + F(F((F(4))!))) + F((0! + F(8)))) \\83419 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 4)) - (F(19))) \\83423 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 3!) \times (F(4))!) + F((F(2) + F(F(3!)))) \\83424 &:= ((8! + ((3!! - 4!) \times 2)) \times F(F(4))) \\83433 &:= ((F(8) + F(3!)) \times ((4 \times 3!!) - 3)) \\83436 &:= (((-F(8)) + 3!!) \times 4) - (-F(3)) \times (F(6))!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83439 &:= (((F(8)^3) + (4)) + 3!) \times 9 \\83444 &:= (((F(8)^3) + F((F(4))!)) \times 4) + F(4!) \\83448 &:= (-8) \times (((F(3!)^{F(4)}) + F(4)) - F(F(8))) \\83454 &:= (F(8) \times ((F(3!)^4) - 5!) - F(F(4))) \\83456 &:= -(((8^{3!}) + ((-4) \times 5!) \times 6!)) \\83460 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(3))) - F((F(4))!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)) \\83462 &:= ((F(8) + F(3!)) \times ((4 \times 6!) - 2)) \\83463 &:= (-((F(8)^3) + ((F(4!) - 6) \times F(3))) \\83464 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - F((F(4))!)) - (F(6)^4)) \\83465 &:= -((F((8 + F(3))) + ((4! - 6!) \times 5!)) \\83466 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - ((4^6) + 6)) \\83468 &:= ((8! - 3!) + (4 \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) \\83472 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - (4^{7-F(2)})) \\83474 &:= ((-8!) + F((F(3) + 4!)) + ((7^4)) \\83475 &:= ((8 + F(F(3))) \times ((F(4!) + 7)/5)) \\83480 &:= (-8) \times (((F(3!)^{F(4)}) - F(F(8))) - 0!) \\83483 &:= (8 - ((-F(3)) \times F(4!)) + (F(8)^3)) \\83493 &:= (-((F(8)^3) + ((F(4!) + 9) \times F(3))) \\83494 &:= (-((F(8) + 3!)) + ((F((F(4))!) + 9)^4)) \\83495 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((-3) - 4!) - (9!/(-5))) \\83496 &:= ((8! \times F(3)) + ((4 \times F(9)) \times F(F(6)))) \\83517 &:= (-F(8)) \times ((3! \times (-5)) - F((1 + F(7)))) \\ \\83520 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 0 \\83521 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 1 \\83522 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 2 \\83523 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 3 \\83524 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 4 \\83525 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 5 \\83526 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 6 \\83527 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 7 \\83528 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 8 \\83529 &:= 8! + 3 \times 5!^2 + 9 \\ \\83531 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F((F(F(3!)) - (5)))) \times (3! + 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83534 &:= ((8 + 3!) + (5! \times (3!! - (4!)))) \\83535 &:= (8! + (3 \times ((5!^{F(3)}) + (5)))) \\83536 &:= -8 + (F(3) - 5!)^{F(3)} \times 6 \\83537 &:= (((-8) + 3!!) \times (5! - 3)) + F(F(7)) \\83538 &:= (F((8 + F(F(3)))) \times ((5! - 3) \times F(8))) \\83538 &:= (F((8 + F(F(3)))) \times ((5! - 3) \times F(8))) \\83540 &:= (F(8) - ((3!! \times (-5! - (4)))) + 0!) \\83541 &:= (F(8) + (3!! \times (5! - (4 \times 1)))) \\83542 &:= (F(8) + ((3!! \times (5! - (4))) + F(2))) \\83543 &:= (F(8) - ((3!! \times (-5! - (4)))) - F(3)) \\83544 &:= ((8! \times F(3)) + ((5! \times 4!) + 4!)) \\83546 &:= (8 - (((-3) + 5!) \times ((F(4))! - (6!)))) \\83549 &:= (F(F(8)) - (((F(3))! / (-5)) - F(4)) \times 9) \\83574 &:= ((F(F(8)) / F(3)) + ((5^7) - 4!)) \\83576 &:= (((F((8 + 3)) \times 5!) - F(F(7))) \times F(6)) \\83584 &:= (8! + ((F(3!) \times (5 + F(8)))^{F(F(4))})) \\83587 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(3!)) + F((-5) + F(8))) \times 7) \\83593 &:= (-8!) - ((F(F(3!)) \times (-5!)) - F((F(9) - F(3!)))) \\83594 &:= (((-8) - ((F(3!))! / 5)) \times (-9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\83607 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(3))) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!)) - F(7)) \\83614 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(3))) \times (F(F(6)) - 1)) - (F(4))!) \\83620 &:= (F((F(8) - F(3))) \times (F((6 + 2)) - 0!)) \\83635 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(3!))) - (-6! \times F(3!))) \times 5) \\83638 &:= ((-F(F(8))) + (F(3!))!) + ((F((6 \times 3)) \times F(8))) \\83638 &:= ((-F(F(8))) + (F(3!))!) + ((F((6 \times 3)) \times F(8))) \\83641 &:= (F(8) - (-F((-F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \times (F(F((F(4))!) - 1))) \\83643 &:= ((-F(8)) + 3!!) + (6 \times (4!^3)) \\83644 &:= (((F(8) - F(F(3))) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))))) + (4!)) \\83647 &:= ((F((8 + 3!)) - (-6 + 4!)) \times F(F(7))) \\83657 &:= (-8!) - (F((F(3) \times (6 + 5))) \times (-7)) \\83663 &:= ((-F(F(8))) + (F(3!))!) + (F((F(F(6)) - F(6)))^{F(3)}) \\83664 &:= ((F(8) \times 3!) \times 664) \\83671 &:= ((8 \times ((-3!!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7)))) - 1 \\83672 &:= (8 \times ((-3!!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(7) \times F(2))))\end{aligned}$$

- 83673** := $((8 \times ((-3!!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(3)))$
83674 := $((8 \times ((-3!!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(4)))$
83677 := $((8! \times F(3)) + F(6)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(7)))$
83678 := $(-8!) + ((F(F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) \times 7) + (F(8)))$
83694 := $(F((8 + 3!)) \times (6 \times (F(9) + F(4))))$
83706 := $(-8!) - (F(F(3!)) \times (7! - F(F(F(06))))))$
83728 := $(8 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) - ((7! \times 2)/F(8)))$
83733 := $((F(8) + 3!!) \times (F(F(7)) - ((F(3) + 3)!))$
83735 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - F(F(7))) - (3!! \times 5)$
83736 := $((F(F(8)) + F(3!)) + F(F(7))) - 3!! \times F(6)$
83742 := $((8! + 3!)/F(7)) - ((F((F(4)!))! \times (-2)))$
83744 := $((F(F(8)) - ((3! + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)))) \times F((F(4)!))$
83747 := $((8! \times F(3)) - ((F(F(7)) + (F(4)!)) \times (-F(7))))$
83748 := $((F(F(8)) - F(-(F(3) - F(7)))) \times 4) + 8!$
83752 := $(-8) - (((F(3!))! + (F(7) \times 5!)) \times (-2))$
83754 := $((F(F(8)) \times 3) - ((7! - 5!)) \times F(4))$
83760 := $((F((F(8) - F(3))) + 7) \times (F(F(6)) - 0!))$
83764 := $((F(F(8)) \times 3!) + (7 \times F((-6) + 4!)))$
83765 := $((8! \times F(3)) + ((F(7) - F(6))^5))$
83773 := $((8! \times F(3)) + (F(7) \times (F(F(7)) + F(3!))))$
83774 := $((F(8) + ((3!! \times F(F(7))) - F(F(7))))/F(F(4)))$
83776 := $((F(F(8)) - 3!!) + F(F(7))) + F(7) \times F(6)$
83780 := $((-8) - F((3! + F(7))) \times (-F(8) - 0!))$
83791 := $-(((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - ((7! \times F(9)) - 1)))$
83792 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - ((7! \times F(9)))) \times (-F(2))$
83793 := $-(((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - ((7! \times F(9)))) - F(F(3)))$
83794 := $-(((F(F(8)) \times F(3!)) - ((7! \times F(9)))) - F(F(4)))$
83795 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(F(3!)) \times F(7)) - (9!/(-5))))$
83834 := $((8! + F((3! + (8 + 3)))) \times F(F(4)))$
83842 := $(8 - (((F(3!))! + F((F(8) - 4)))) \times (-2))$
83847 := $(8! + (((-3!) + F(F(8))) \times 4) - F(F(7)))$
83848 := $((-((F(8)^{F(3)})) + F(F(8))) - (4!)) \times 8$
83853 := $(-F(8)) - (((3!! - F(8))) \times (-5!)) + 3!$
83865 := $-(((F(8) - 3!) + ((F(8) - 6!) \times 5!))$
83867 := $-((((8 - 3)! \times (F(8) - 6!)) + F(7)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83872 &:= (- (8) - ((3!! - (F(8))) \times (-((7 - 2)!))) \\
 83874 &:= (((- (F(8)) + 3!!) \times ((- (8) + F(7)))!) - (F(4))!) \\
 83875 &:= (((- (F(8)) + 3!!) \times ((- (8) + F(7)))!) - (5)) \\
 83880 &:= ((- (F(8)) + 3!!) \times ((- (8) + F((8 - 0!))))!) \\
 83884 &:= (8! - ((F((F(3) + 8)) - F(F(8))) \times 4)) \\
 83944 &:= (8! + (((3!! - F(9)) \times (-4)) + F(4!))) \\
 83948 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 39) \times 4) + 8!) \\
 83964 &:= (8! - (((F(F(3)) + F(9)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 4)) \\
 83967 &:= (((- (F(8)) \times F(F(3))) - (-9) \times 6!) \times F(7)) \\
 83973 &:= (((F(8) - (3!! \times 9)) \times (-F(7))) + 3!) \\
 83979 &:= (8! + (((F(F(3!)) \times 9) - (7!)) \times (-9))) \\
 83984 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 3!!) + (F(9) \times 8)) \times F((F(4))!)) \\
 83997 &:= ((F((F(8) - F(3))) \times 9) + F(((-9) + F(7))!)) \\
 84032 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (0! + (F(F(3!))²))) \\
 84034 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F((F(4))!)^{-0!+3!})) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 84035 &:= ((8 - F(4)) \times ((0! + 3!)⁵)) \\
 84048 &:= (((((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) - 0!) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-8)) \\
 84048 &:= (((((F(8)^{F(F(4))}) - 0!) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-8)) \\
 84050 &:= (((8!/4!) + 0!) \times 50) \\
 84064 &:= ((8! - 40) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 4)) \\
 84068 &:= (8! + (4 \times (-((0! + F(6))) + F(F(8)))))) \\
 84069 &:= (((((F(F(8)) \times 4) - 0!) + (F(6))!) - F(9)) \\
 84076 &:= (8! + (4 \times ((0 - 7) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 84083 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) - F(08)) + (F(3!))!) \\
 84084 &:= (8! + (((- (4) - 0!) + F(F(8))) \times 4)) \\
 84087 &:= (8! - ((4 \times (0! - F(F(8)))) + F(7))) \\
 84094 &:= (- (F(F(8))) + (((F(4))!)! \times ((0! - F(9)) \times (-4)))) \\
 84096 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + ((0! - 9))) + (F(6))!) \\
 84097 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (-((0! - 9)))!) - 7) \\
 84103 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) - 1) + (F((03)!))!) \\
 84104 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (F((10 - 4))!)) \\
 84105 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + 1) + (F((0! + (5))))!) \\
 84106 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (1 + 0!)) + (F(6))!) \\
 84108 &:= (8! + (4 \times (1 + F(F(08))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 84128** := $(8! + (4 \times (((1 + 2))! + F(F(8)))))$
84136 := $((((F(F(8)) + F((F(4))!)) \times (1 + 3)) + (F(6))!))$
84138 := $((((F(F(8)) \times 4) + F((1 + F(3!)))) + 8!))$
84139 := $((((F(F(8)) \times 4) + 1) + (F(3!))!) + F(9))$
84146 := $((F((F(8) - (F(4))!)) \times ((1 + 4))!) + F(F(F(6))))$
84168 := $((F(8) \times 4!) \times (-1 + (F(6) \times F(8))))$
84184 := $(8! + ((F(F((F(4))!)) - (1 - F(F(8)))) \times 4))$
84188 := $(8! + (4 \times (F((1 \times 8)) + F(F(8)))))$
84235 := $((8! \times F(F(4))) - ((F(2) - 3!!) \times 5))$
84237 := $((((8! - ((F(4))!)) \times 2) - (3 - 7!))$
84240 := $((((8! - ((F(4))!)) \times 2) + (((F(4))! + 0!))!))$
84245 := $((8! \times F(F(4))) - ((F(2) + ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)))$
84247 := $((((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) + F(2)) + F(4!)) + (7!))$
84248 := $((8! + F((4!/2))) - (-4 \times F(F(8))))$
84248 := $((8! + F((4!/2))) - (-4 \times F(F(8))))$
84249 := $((((8!/4) + F(2)) - ((F(4))!)) \times 9)$
84252 := $((F(8) \times F((F(4)^2))) \times (5! - 2))$
84256 := $(((-8!) - F((F(4))!)) \times (-2)) + (5 \times 6!))$
84264 := $((((F(F(8)) \times (4!/2)) - (6!)) - F(4!))$
84267 := $((-8!) - F((4! - 2))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(7)))$
84274 := $((((8! \times ((F(4))!)) - 2) / (-F(F(7)))) - (F((F(4))!))!)$
84288 := $((8 \times 4!) \times (-2) + (F(8) \times F(8)))$
84324 := $(8! + (4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F((2 + F((F(4))!))))))$
84332 := $((((F(8) - F(4!)) + F((-F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) \times (-2))$
84336 := $((((F(8) \times 4!) - F(3)) \times F(3!)) \times F(F(6)))$
84337 := $((((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (F((3 + 3))!)) + F(F(7)))$
84344 := $((((8^{F(4)!}) - 3!!) / F(F(4))) - F(4!))$
84345 := $((8! \times F(F(4))) - ((F(F(3!)) + ((F(4))!)) \times (-5)))$
84346 := $(((-F(8)) + ((F(4))!)) \times (-3!! + 4)) / (-6)$
84347 := $(-F(8) - (-F(F(4))) \times ((F(3!))! - (F((F(4))!)) \times (-F(F(7))))))$
84353 := $((-F(8) - (F(4!) \times (-3))) + (-5 \times F(F(F(3!))))$
84354 := $((((F(8) - (4)) - 3!!) \times (-5!)) - (F(4))!)$
84355 := $((((F(8) - (4)) - 3!!) \times (-5!)) - (5))$
84357 := $(8! + ((4 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (5))) + F(F(7))))$
84360 := $((-((F(8) - (4))) + 3!!) \times ((6 - 0!))!)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84372 &:= (((8! + F(F(4))) + (F(3!) \times F(F(7)))) \times 2) \\
 84374 &:= ((F(((8 - 4)!)) - F((3! + F(7)))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 84375 &:= ((F(8) + (F(4)!)) \times (-((F(3) - (7)))^5)) \\
 84376 &:= (8 + (F(F(4)) \times ((F(3!) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6)!))) \\
 84378 &:= (F(8) \times ((4^3!) - 78)) \\
 84382 &:= (8 - ((F(4!) - F(-((F(3) - F(8)))))) \times (-2)) \\
 84384 &:= ((8! + F(4!)) - ((3! \times 8)^{F(F(4))})) \\
 84385 &:= (F((F(8) + (4))) + (3!! \times (8 + 5))) \\
 84386 &:= (F(F(8)) - (((4! - (3! \times F(8))) \times 6!)) \\
 84392 &:= (8! + (((F(4))!^{3!}) - F((9 \times 2)))) \\
 84394 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F((F(4)!)) - (3!! \times (-F(9) \times F(4)))) \\
 84396 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(4)!)) + (3!! \times (F(9) - F(6)))) \\
 84429 &:= (((F(8)^{F(4)}) + ((F(4) + 2)!)) \times 9) \\
 84432 &:= (((8!/F(F((F(4)!)))) - (4! - (F(3)!))!) \times 2) \\
 84433 &:= ((F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) + (F(4!)/3)) + (F(3)!))! \\
 84437 &:= (F((F(8) + (4))) - ((4 + 3!!) \times (-F(7)))) \\
 84439 &:= -((F(F((F(8)/F(4)))) - ((F(4!) \times (-3!)) + 9!)) \\
 84443 &:= (-((F(8) - (44^{F(4)}))) - 3!!) \\
 84444 &:= ((8! + ((-F(4!)) + ((F(4)!))!)/(-4!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 84448 &:= (((8!/(F(4)!)))/(-F(4)) + F(4!)) + 8! \\
 84448 &:= (((8!/(F(4)!)))/(-F(4)) + F(4!)) + 8! \\
 84449 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F(4) \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - (((F(4)!))! \times (-F(9)))))) \\
 84453 &:= (((F(8) + ((F(4)!))!) \times (-((F(4)! - 5!))) - F(F(3!))) \\
 84454 &:= (((8 + ((F(4)!))!) \times (-4 + 5!)) + (F(4)!)) \\
 84456 &:= (-((F(8) \times 4!)) + ((F(F(4)) - 5!) \times (-6!))) \\
 84457 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (F((F(4)!))!)) - (-5! - F(F(7)))) \\
 84462 &:= ((8! + ((F(4!)/4!) - F(F(6)))) \times 2) \\
 84464 &:= (((F(8) + F(F(F(4))))^{F(4)}) \times F(6)) - ((F(4)!))! \\
 84467 &:= (((8! \times 44)/F(F(6))) - F(7)) \\
 84474 &:= ((F(8) + ((F(4)!))!) \times (((F(4)! + F(7)) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 \\
 84480 &:= 8! \times 44/F(8) + 0 \\
 84481 &:= 8! \times 44/F(8) + 1 \\
 84482 &:= 8! \times 44/F(8) + 2 \\
 84483 &:= 8! \times 44/F(8) + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$84484 := 8! \times 44 / F(8) + 4$$

$$84485 := 8! \times 44 / F(8) + 5$$

$$84486 := 8! \times 44 / F(8) + 6$$

$$84487 := 8! \times 44 / F(8) + 7$$

$$84488 := 8! \times 44 / F(8) + 8$$

$$84489 := 8! \times 44 / F(8) + 9$$

$$84494 := (8! + (((F(4))!)! \times (-F(4))) + (-F(9) + F(4!)))$$

$$84496 := ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4))!)) - ((F(F(4)))^9 \times 6))$$

$$84504 := ((8! + (F(4!)/(5 - 0!))!) \times F(F(4)))$$

$$84528 := (8! + (((F(4))!)^5 / 2) + 8!)$$

$$84533 := (((8! + F(4!)) + (5)) - (3 \times 3!))$$

$$84536 := ((8 + F(4!)) - (-53 \times 6!))$$

$$84543 := -((F(8) - ((-4) + 5!) \times (F(4)^{3!})))$$

$$84544 := ((-((8 \times 4^5)) + F(4!)) + F(4!))$$

$$84546 := (((8! / F(F(4))) / 5) - (F(4)!)) \times F(F(6))$$

$$84547 := (((8 \times (F(4))!) - (5))^{F(4)} + (7!))$$

$$84563 := -((F((F(8) - (4))) - (5! \times (6! - F(3))))))$$

$$84564 := (((F(F(8)) - (F((F(4))!)^5)) \times (-6)) - F(4!))$$

$$84568 := (-(((F(8) + (4)) \times 5!) + (F(6) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$84573 := -((F((-8) + 4!) - (5! \times (-7) + 3!)))$$

$$84576 := (((F(F(8)) - F(F((F(4))!))) + (-5!) - F(F(7))) \times F(6))$$

$$84577 := (F((F(8) + F(F(4)))) - (-5!) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(7))))$$

$$84579 := ((-F(8) + ((F(4))!)!) \times (5! + F(-(7 - 9))))$$

$$84580 := (8! + (4 \times ((5! + F(F(8))) - 0!))$$

$$84582 := (8! + ((4 \times (5! + F(F(8)))) - 2))$$

$$84583 := (8! + ((4 \times (5! + F(F(8)))) - F(F(3))))$$

$$84584 := (((8! / 4) + 5!) + F(F(8))) \times 4$$

$$84588 := (8! - ((-4) \times F((-5) + F(8))) - 8!)$$

$$84592 := (((8 + F(4!)) - (5! \times F(9))) \times 2)$$

$$84594 := (((-F(8) + ((F(4))!)!) \times 5!) + (F(9) \times F(F((F(4))!))))$$

$$84609 := (-F(8)) \times (F(4) + ((F(6))! / (-0! + 9)))$$

$$84624 := (((F(8)^{F(4)}) \times F(6)) - 2) \times 4!$$

$$84630 := ((8 + (F(4))!) \times (-6! + F((F(F(3!)) - 0!)))$$

$$84637 := ((8! \times 4) - ((F(F(F(6))) + 3) \times 7))$$

$$\begin{aligned}84639 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(4))!) - ((6! - (3^9)))) \\84644 &:= ((-8) - (F(4))!) \times (((F(6))! - F(4!)) + F(F(4))) \\84648 &:= (((F(8) \times 4!) \times F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times 8 \\84648 &:= (((F(8) \times 4!) \times F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times 8 \\84649 &:= (-F(8)) + (((F(4!) \times (-6)) - F(F(4))) + 9!) \\84656 &:= -(((8! + 4!) - (F(6) \times (5^6)))) \\84659 &:= (-8) - ((F(4!) \times 6) + (5 - 9!)) \\84664 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(4)) \times F(6)) + (6! \times (-4))) \\84666 &:= (((8! - F(4!)) \times (-6) - F(6)) - 6) \\84667 &:= (-F(F(8))) + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times ((6! \times 6) + F(F(7)))) \\84671 &:= (((-8!) + F(4!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7)) - 1 \\84672 &:= ((8! - F(4 \times 6)) \times (-7 \times 2)) \\84673 &:= (((-8!) + F(4!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7)) + F(F(3)) \\84674 &:= (((-8!) + F(4!)) \times (F(F(6)) - 7)) + F(F(4)) \\84675 &:= -((F((F(8) - F(F(F(4)))))) - (6! \times (7 + 5!))) \\84679 &:= ((F(((8 - 4))!)) \times (-6)) + (7 + 9!) \\84680 &:= (8 \times (((-4!) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(8))) + 0!) \\84684 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(F(F(4)))) - (6! - F(F(8)))) \times 4) \\84688 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((-4) \times 6!) / (-8)) \times 8) \\84692 &:= (F(8) - ((F(4!) \times 6) - ((9! - F(2)))) \\84693 &:= (F(8) + (((F(4!) \times (-6)) + 9!) \times F(F(3)))) \\84694 &:= ((F(8) + ((F(4!) \times (-6)) + 9!)) + F(F(F(4)))) \\84696 &:= (8 \times (F(4) + (F(F(6)) \times (9!/6!))) \\84704 &:= ((8 \times (4^7)) - F((04)!)) \\84723 &:= (((8^4) - F(7)) - (-2) \times (F(3!)!)) \\84734 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (7!/F(3!))) + (F((F(4))!))!)) \\84735 &:= ((-F(8)) + (-4!) \times (F(7) - 3!)) \times 5) \\84736 &:= ((8^4) + ((7! \times F(3)) \times F(6))) \\84737 &:= (-F(F(8))) + (((F(4))! \times (7! + F(F(F(3!)))))) - F(F(7))) \\84738 &:= -((F(F(8)) + ((-4) + 7!) \times (F(3) - F(8)))) \\84743 &:= ((8! \times F(F(4))) + (7 + (4^3!))) \\84744 &:= (((F(8) \times 4!) \times 7) + F(4)) \times 4! \\84745 &:= ((F(8) - (4)) \times (7! - F((F(F(4)) \times 5)))) \\84746 &:= ((-8!) \times F(F(4))) + (((F(7))! / (F((F(4))!))!)) + F(F(F(6))) \\84747 &:= ((((-F(8)) + F(F(4))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times F(7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84752 &:= (((8 + ((F(4))!)!) \times (-F(F(7)))) + 5!) / (-2) \\
 84757 &:= (8 - ((F(4)!)/(-7)) - (5^7)) \\
 84762 &:= ((8^4) - ((-F(7)) - (F(6))!) \times 2) \\
 84765 &:= (F(8) + (F((F(4))!) \times ((-F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5!)) \\
 84767 &:= (-8) - (((4)! \times (-7)) / (F(F(6))!) + F(F(7))) \\
 84768 &:= ((8! + F(4!)) - ((7! \times F(6)) / F(8))) \\
 84770 &:= (((8! - F(4!)) - 7) \times (-F(7) + 0!)) \\
 84772 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(7) - F(2)))) \\
 84776 &:= -((F(F(8)) + ((F(F(4)) - 7!) \times (F(7) + (6)))) \\
 84777 &:= ((F((-8) + 4!)) \times (F(7) \times 7)) - (7!) \\
 84782 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(4))!) + (F(F(7)) \times 82)) \\
 84784 &:= (F(((8 - 4))!) + (((-7) + F(8))^4)) \\
 84792 &:= (((8! - F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-9))) \times 2) \\
 84798 &:= (8! + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times ((F(F(7)) \times 9) + (F(8)))) \\
 84812 &:= (((8 + ((F(4))!)!) \times F(F((8 - 1)))) / 2) \\
 84814 &:= (-F(F(8))) - ((F(F(4)) - (F(8))) \times ((1 + (F(4))!)!)) \\
 84819 &:= ((8! - F(F(4))) + ((8! + F(19)))) \\
 84820 &:= (((8! \times F(F(4))) + F((F(8) - 2))) - 0!) \\
 84821 &:= ((8! \times F(F(4))) + F((F(8) - (2 \times 1)))) \\
 84822 &:= (((8! \times F(F(4))) + F((F(8) - 2))) + F(2)) \\
 84823 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + ((8! - F(2)))) + 3!!) \\
 84824 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (8! + ((2 + 4))!)) \\
 84825 &:= (F((8 + (F(4))!)) \times (-8 + F(F((2 + 5)))) \\
 84826 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) + ((8! + 2) + 6!)) \\
 84833 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (8! + (3^3!))) \\
 84834 &:= (((8! / F(4)) - F(8)) + 3!!) \times (F(4))! \\
 84836 &:= (8! + ((4 \times (F(F(8)) + 3)) + (6!))) \\
 84837 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 4) + 8!) + 3!!) + F(7) \\
 84840 &:= ((F(8) \times F((F(4))!)) \times ((F(8) \times 4!) + 0!)) \\
 84842 &:= (((F(8) \times (F(4))!) - 8) \times (((F(4))!)! - F(2))) \\
 84845 &:= (((8! + 4!) + 8!) + F((4! - (5)))) \\
 84847 &:= (((((F(8))! + (4))!) / (F(8))!) - (4!)) \times 7) \\
 84856 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(4) + (8! / 5!))) \times F(6)) \\
 84859 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (F(8) \times (5! + 9))) \\
 84861 &:= ((-F(8)) + ((4)! / (F(8))!)) \times (6 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$84863 := (F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) - ((-8!) - F(F(6))) \times F(3)))$$

$$84864 := (((F(8)^{F(4)}) \times 8) + F(6)) \times 4!$$

$$84865 := ((((-8!) + F(4!)) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) \times 5$$

$$84866 := ((((-8!)/(F(4)!)) + F(F(8))) + (F(6)!)) + (F(6)!))$$

$$84872 := (8 \times (((F(4)!)/8) + F(7))^2)$$

$$84875 := ((F(F(8)) - ((F(4!)/(-8)) - F(F(7)))) \times 5$$

$$84876 := (8! + ((4 \times (F(F(8)) + F(7))) + (6!)))$$

$$84879 := (8! + ((F((F(4) + 8)) - (7!)) \times (-9)))$$

$$84882 := (F((-8) + 4!)) \times (88 - 2)$$

$$84923 := (((-8) - F(4!)) + (9! \times 2))/F(3!))$$

$$84924 := (-((F(((8 - 4)!)) - (9! \times 2)))/F((F(4)!))$$

$$84925 := (F(F(8)) + (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^2) - (5)))$$

$$84928 := (-8) \times (((F(4)! \times F((9 + F(2)))) - F(F(8))))$$

$$84930 := (F(F(8)) - (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^{F(3)}) \times (-0!)))$$

$$84931 := (F(F(8)) + (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^{F(3)}) + 1))$$

$$84932 := ((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) + ((F(9) \times F(3!))^2))$$

$$84933 := ((F(F(8)) + F(4)) + ((F(9) \times F(3!))^{F(3)}))$$

$$84934 := ((F(F(8)) + 4) + ((F(9) \times F(3!))^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$84935 := (F(F(8)) + (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^{F(3)}) + (5)))$$

$$84936 := ((8! - 4!) + ((9!/F(3!)) - (6!)))$$

$$84937 := (F(F(8)) + (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^{F(3)}) + 7))$$

$$84938 := (F(F(8)) + (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^{F(3)}) + 8))$$

$$84939 := (F(F(8)) + (((F((F(4)!)) \times F(9))^{F(3)}) + 9))$$

$$84944 := (((-8) - ((F(4)!))!) + ((F(9)^{F(4)}) + F(4!)))$$

$$84945 := (-F(8)) \times ((4 \times F(9)) - F((4! - (5))))$$

$$84947 := (((-8) \times ((F(4)!))!) + ((9!/4) - F(7)))$$

$$84949 := ((F(8) - F(F(4))) \times (-9 - ((F((F(4)!))!)/(-9))))$$

$$84952 := (-8) - (((-((F(4) - 9)))! \times (-5! - 2)))$$

$$84954 := (((F(8) - ((F(4)!))!) - 9) \times (-5!)) - (F(4)!)$$

$$84955 := (((F(8) - ((F(4)!))!) - 9) \times (-5!)) - (5)$$

$$84960 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 0$$

$$84961 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 1$$

$$84962 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 2$$

$$84963 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 3$$

$$84964 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 4$$

$$84965 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 5$$

$$84966 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 6$$

$$84967 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 7$$

$$84968 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 8$$

$$84969 := (F(8) \times 4 + F(9)) \times 6! + 9$$

$$84974 := ((8! + F(4!)) - (F(9) + (7!/F(4))))$$

$$84975 := ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4)!)) - (9 + F((F(7) + (5))))))$$

$$84984 := ((F(F(8)) \times (F(4) + 9)) - F(((8 - 4)!))$$

$$84993 := ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4)!)) - (-9 + F((9 \times F(3))))))$$

$$84994 := ((-8) \times ((F(4)!)) + (F(9) - (9!/(-4))))$$

$$84997 := ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4)!)) - (F((9 + 9)) - F(7)))$$

$$85034 := (F(F(8)) + ((50 - F(3!))^{F(4)}))$$

$$85048 := (-((F(8) \times 5!)) + (F((F(04)!)) \times F(F(8))))$$

$$85144 := (8 \times (-5) + ((1 + F(F((F(4)!))))^{F(4)}))$$

$$85183 := (8! + ((5! - 1) \times F((8 + 3!))))$$

$$85243 := (((F(F(8)) + F((5^2))) - ((F(4)!)) - F(3!))$$

$$85245 := (-((F(8) \times F((5 \times 2)))) - (((F(4)!)) \times (-5!)))$$

$$85246 := (((F(F(8)) - 5) + F((F(2) + 4!))) - (6!))$$

$$85247 := (((8! \times 5) - F((2 + 4!))) + (7!))$$

$$85248 := ((((((8 - 5)!)) \times (-2)) + F(4!)) + 8!)$$

$$85251 := (F(F(8)) + (F((5^2)) - ((5 + 1)!))$$

$$85256 := (F(F(8)) + ((5 + F(25)) - 6!))$$

$$85260 := (-F(8) \times ((5! - F((-2) + F(F(6)))) + 0!))$$

$$85264 := (8! + ((F(F((5 + 2))) - F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}))$$

$$85274 := (F(F(8)) - ((-5!) \times F((F(2) \times F(7)))) - F(4!))$$

$$85280 := ((-F(8)) \times (5! - F((-2) + F(8)))) - 0!$$

$$85281 := (-F(8) \times (5! - F((-2) + F((8 \times 1))))))$$

$$85282 := ((-F(8)) \times (5! - F((-2) + F(8)))) + F(2)$$

$$85283 := ((-F(8)) \times (5! - F((-2) + F(8)))) + F(3)$$

$$85284 := ((-F(8)) \times (5! - F((-2) + F(8)))) + F(4)$$

$$85286 := (8 - ((5! + 2) \times (F(8) - 6!)))$$

$$85323 := (-F(8) \times ((5! - F(3)) - F((-2) + F(F(3!))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 85328 &:= (8 - (- (5!) \times (3!! - (F(2) + 8)))) \\
 85335 &:= (8! + ((F((5^{F(3)})) \times 3)/5)) \\
 85337 &:= (- (F(8)) - ((- (5) - (3^{F(3!)})) \times F(7))) \\
 85341 &:= (F(8) - (5! \times ((F(3!) - ((F(4)!)!) + 1))) \\
 85344 &:= -(((8!/5!) \times (F(3) - (4^4)))) \\
 85350 &:= ((F((F(8) - (5))) + 3!!) \times 50) \\
 85361 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((5 + 3!) \times F((F(F(6)) - 1)))) \\
 85363 &:= (((F(8) \times (-5)) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(3!))) \\
 85366 &:= (F(F(8)) - (-((5! + F(3))) \times F((F(F(6)) - 6)))) \\
 85376 &:= (8 \times ((5! \times F(-((F(3) - F(7)))))) - F(6)) \\
 85384 &:= (((- (F(8)) \times F((5 + F(3)))) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)!)) \\
 85389 &:= ((8! - F(((5 + F(3)) + F(8)))) + 9!) \\
 85399 &:= (((- ((F(8) \times 5!)) + F(3!)) \times (-F(9))) - 9) \\
 85407 &:= (- (F(8)) \times ((- (5!) \times F((F((F(4)!) + 0!))) + F(7))) \\
 85408 &:= ((- ((F(8) \times 5!)) + F((F(4)!)!)) \times (-F((0! + 8)))) \\
 85413 &:= -((F((F(8) - (5))) + (-(((4 + 1)!) \times 3!))) \\
 85419 &:= (- (F(8)) - (- (5!) \times (((F(4)!)!) + ((1 - 9)))) \\
 85428 &:= (F(8) \times (5! - (- (4) \times F((2 \times 8)))) \\
 85431 &:= (- (8) - ((5! \times (F((F(4)!) - (3!))) + 1)) \\
 85432 &:= (- (8) - (5! \times (((F(4)!) - 3!) + 2))) \\
 85433 &:= (- (8) - ((5! \times (F((F(4)!) - (3!))) - F(F(3)))) \\
 85434 &:= (((8 \times 5!) \times F((F(4) + F(3!)))) - (F(4)!) \\
 85435 &:= (((8 \times 5!) \times F((F(4) + F(3!)))) - (5)) \\
 85437 &:= (((8! - 5!) \times F(F(4))) - (3 - 7!)) \\
 85439 &:= (8 - ((5! \times (F((F(4)!) - (3!))) + 9)) \\
 \\
 85440 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 0 \\
 85441 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 1 \\
 85442 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 2 \\
 85443 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 3 \\
 85444 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 4 \\
 85445 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 5 \\
 85446 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 6 \\
 85447 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 7 \\
 85448 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 85449 &:= 8 \times 5! \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) + 9 \\ 85456 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (((5! + 4!) + 5!))) \times F(6)) \\ 85460 &:= (F(8) - ((5! \times (F((F(4))!) - (6!))) + 0!)) \\ 85461 &:= (F(8) - (5! \times (F((F(4))!) + (6! \times (-1)))))) \\ 85462 &:= (F(8) - ((5! \times (F((F(4))!) - (6!))) - F(2))) \\ 85463 &:= (F(8) + ((5! - F(F(F(4)))) \times (6! - F(3)))) \\ 85464 &:= (((8 \times 5!) \times F((F(4) + F(6)))) + (4!)) \\ 85475 &:= (-85) + (((F(4))!)! - 7) \times 5! \\ 85476 &:= (((F(8) \times 5!) - (F(4))!) \times (F(7) + F(F(6)))) \\ 85524 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - (5 \times ((5 + 2)!)) \times (F(4))!)) \\ 85527 &:= -(((F(8) - (5! \times F((5 \times 2)))) \times F(7))) \\ 85533 &:= -((F((F(8) - (5))) + (-5! \times (F(F(3)) + 3!)))) \\ 85536 &:= (((8 - 5)!^5) \times (3 + F(6))) \\ 85538 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F((5!/5))) - (-3) \times 8!) \\ 85539 &:= (-((F(8) + 5!)) + ((-5!) \times F(F(3!))) \times (-F(9))) \\ 85545 &:= (-855) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-5!)) \\ 85547 &:= ((F(F((8 - 5))) + 5!) \times (((F(4))!)! - F(7))) \\ 85554 &:= (-((F(8) - ((5! \times 5!) - 5!))) \times (F(4))!) \\ 85561 &:= ((F(F((8 - 5))) - 5!) \times (-6! - 1)) \\ 85576 &:= ((F(8) - (5)) - (5! \times (7 - 6!))) \\ 85584 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (((5! + 5!) + 8))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\ 85596 &:= ((F(8) \times (-5) + (5! \times F(9)))) + F(F(6)) \\ 85638 &:= -((F(8) - ((5! \times (6! - 3!)) - F(8))) \\ 85648 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (5! \times (6 - 4))) \times 8) \\ 85654 &:= (-((F(8) - ((5! \times 6!) - (5)))) - ((F(4))!)! \\ 85656 &:= (8 - (((-5!) + F(F(F(6)))) - 5!) \times (-F(6))) \\ 85659 &:= (F(8) \times ((5 - 6) + (5! \times F(9)))) \\ 85660 &:= -((F(8) - (((5! \times 6!) - 6!) + 0!)) \\ 85667 &:= (((8! - 5)) + (F(6))!) - ((F(6) - 7!)) \\ 85672 &:= (-8) + (5! \times ((6! - 7) + F(2))) \\ 85673 &:= (((8! - 5)) + (F(6))!) + ((7! - F(3))) \\ 85674 &:= ((((-8) + 5!) \times 6!) + 7!) - (F(4))! \\ 85678 &:= ((8! - F((-5) + F(6))) + (7! + 8!)) \\ 85680 &:= (8! + (5! \times (F((6 + 8)) + 0!))) \end{aligned}$$

- 85683** := $(-(F(8)) - ((5 - F((F(6) + F(8)))))/3!))$
85688 := $((F(F(8)) + (5)) \times F(6) - (8!/F(8)))$
85693 := $(-(F(8) - ((5! \times 6!) + F(9)))) - 3!!$
85694 := $((8! - ((5! \times F(6)) + F(9))) + F(4!))$
85695 := $((-F(8) + (((5 + F(6)))!/9!)) \times 5)$
85696 := $(8! + (((5! + F(6)) + 9!)/F(6)))$
85704 := $((F(F(8)) - F((5 + 7) + 0!)) \times F((F(4)!))$
85722 := $(F(8) \times ((5! \times F((7 + 2))) + 2))$
85734 := $(((-8) \times (5! - 7!)) + 3!) + F(4!))$
85737 := $((((F(F(8)) + (5)) - F(F(7))) \times F(3!)) - 7)$
85743 := $(-F(8) \times ((-5!) \times F((F(7) - (4)))) - 3))$
85749 := $((8! - 5!) + ((7! + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times 9))$
85768 := $-((F(((8 - 5)!)) \times ((F(F(7)) - F(6)) - F(F(8))))))$
85784 := $((8! - ((5! - (7)) \times 8)) + F(4!))$
85785 := $(F(8) \times (5 + ((F(7) + F(8)) \times 5!)))$
85787 := $((((8! + 5!) - F(7)) + 8!) + 7!)$
85791 := $(-8) - (((5 \times (F(7)!)))/(-9!)) + 1))$
85792 := $((-8) + 5!) + ((7! \times F(9))/2)$
85793 := $(-8) - (((5 \times (F(7)!)))/(-9!)) - F(F(3)))$
85794 := $((8! + 5!) + (7! \times 9)) - (F(4)!)$
85799 := $(8 - (((5 \times (F(7)!)))/(-9!)) + 9))$
85806 := $(-F(8)) \times ((-5!) \times F((8 + 0!))) - 6))$
85826 := $(F(F(8)) - (((-5) \times F(8)) + F(2)) \times 6!))$
85827 := $(-F(8)) \times ((-5!) \times F((8 + F(2)))) - 7))$
85836 := $((F(F(8)) \times 5) + (8!/F(3))) + F(F(F(6))))$
85843 := $((F(F(8)) - 5!) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(3!))$
85846 := $((F(F(8)))/(-5 + 8)) + F(4!)) + (F(6)!)$
85851 := $((F(F(8)) - 5!) + F((F(8) + (5 - 1))))$
85854 := $((F(8) \times (-5) - F(8)) - (-5!) \times ((F(4)!)!))$
85864 := $((F(F(8)) - 5!) \times 8) - ((6! + 4!))$
85869 := $(-F(8)) \times (-5!) - ((-F(8)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-9!))$
85870 := $((F((F(8) - (5)))) \times 87) + 0!)$
85894 := $((F(F(8)) - 5!) \times 8) - (F(9) \times F(F((F(4)!))))$
85896 := $((F(F(8)) - (5! + (89))) \times F(6))$
85911 := $(F(8) \times ((5! \times F(9)) + 11))$

$$\begin{aligned} 85913 &:= (((F(8) \times 5!) \times F(9)) + F(13)) \\ 85932 &:= (F(8) \times ((5! \times F(9)) + (3! \times 2))) \\ 85934 &:= ((8! - (F((5 + 9)) \times F(3))) + F(4!)) \\ 85935 &:= (((8! + 5!) \times F(9)) / (F(F(3!)) - (5))) \\ 85936 &:= (((F(8) \times 5!) \times F(9)) + (F(3)^{F(6)})) \\ 85942 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (5 - F(9))) + F((4! + F(2)))) \\ 85944 &:= (((8! + F((-((5 - 9))!)) - ((F(4)!)!) - (4!)) \\ 85953 &:= (-F(8) \times (-((5! \times F(9)) - F((5 + F(3)))))) \\ 85956 &:= (((((8 - 5))!)! + F(9)) \times (5! - (6))) \\ 85963 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F(5^{F(9-6)})) - F(3!)) \\ 85964 &:= (((8! + ((5 - 9))) - 6!) + F(4!)) \\ 85968 &:= (F((((8 + 5) - 9)!) - (6! - 8!)) \\ 85970 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((F(5^{9-7}) - 0!))) \\ 85994 &:= (((F(8) \times 5!) + 9) \times F(9)) + F((F(4)!)!) \\ 86016 &:= (F(8) \times (((6 - 0!) - 1)^6)) \\ 86024 &:= (8 + (F(F(6)) \times (F(((0! + 2)!)^4))) \\ 86037 &:= (((8 + F(6)) + 0!) \times (F(F(3!)) + (7!))) \\ 86043 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!))) + (4!)) \times 3) \\ 86113 &:= (8! + ((F(F(F(6)))/(1 + 1)) + (F(3!)!)) \\ 86136 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6)) + 1)) - ((F(3) \times 6!))) \\ 86152 &:= ((8 - 6!) \times ((-1 - 5!) \times F(2))) \\ 86153 &:= (((8 - 6!) \times (-1 - 5!)) + F(F(3))) \\ 86154 &:= (((8 - 6!) \times (-1 - 5!)) + F(F(4))) \\ 86167 &:= ((((-8) + F((6 + 1)))! \times 6!) - F(F(7))) \\ 86204 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) + F((0! + 4!))) \\ 86224 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(F(6)) \times F((F((2 + 2))!))) \times F((F(4)!)!) \\ 86235 &:= (-((F(8) + F((6 \times 2)))) - (3!! \times (-5!))) \\ 86244 &:= (8! - (((F(F(6))^2) + F(4)) - F(4!))) \\ 86246 &:= ((((-F(8)) \times F(F(6))) - F(2)) + F(4!)) + (F(6)!) \\ 86247 &:= (8! - (((F(6) + F(2))^4) \times (-7))) \\ 86248 &:= (((-8) \times F((F(6) + 2))) + F(4!)) + 8! \\ 86253 &:= -((F(8) - (((6! - F(2)) \times 5!) - 3!)) \\ 86255 &:= ((8! \times (6 - 2)) - F((5 \times 5))) \\ 86256 &:= ((8! - 6!) + ((F(2) + (5))^6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}86265 &:= -F(8) + 6 - (F(2) - 6!) \times 5! \\86272 &:= (-8) + ((6! - F(2)) \times ((7 - 2)!)) \\86274 &:= (((-8!) - F(F(6))) \times (-2)) - (F(F(7)) \times (-4!)) \\86294 &:= ((8! - ((6!/2) + F(9))) + F(4!)) \\86307 &:= (((F(8) \times (-6)) + F((F(F(3!)) - 0!))) \times F(7)) \\86311 &:= (8! + (F((F(F(6)) - F(3))) \times 11)) \\86314 &:= (-86) + (3!! \times ((1 + 4)!)) \\86324 &:= (8! + (((-6!) - F(3!))/2) + F(4!)) \\86334 &:= ((8! - ((6!/F(3)) - 3!)) + F(4!)) \\86335 &:= (((-8) \times F(6)) - F(F(3))) - (3!! \times (-5!)) \\86336 &:= (((F(8) - 6) \times 3!) - F(3!)) \times F(6) \\86344 &:= (-((8!/6!)) + ((3!!^{F(F(4))})/(F(4)!)) \\86345 &:= ((8 - 63) - (((F(4)!))! \times (-5!)) \\86346 &:= ((8! + (F(6)!)) - ((3!! - F(4!))/F(6))) \\86348 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F((F(6) + 3!))) + F((4 + F(8)))) \\86351 &:= (-((8 \times 6)) + ((3!! \times 5!) - 1)) \\86352 &:= (-((8 \times 6)) + (3! \times (5!^2))) \\86353 &:= (-((8 \times 6)) - ((3!! \times (-5!)) - F(F(3)))) \\86354 &:= (-((8 \times 6)) + ((3!! \times 5!) + F(F(4)))) \\86356 &:= ((-8) - (6^{F(3)})) + (5! \times 6!) \\86357 &:= (-((8!/6!)) - ((3!! \times (-5!)) - F(7))) \\86358 &:= (-F(8) - (((((6 - 3)!))! \times (-5!)) + (F(8)))) \\86364 &:= (((F(8) \times 6!) - 3!) - 6!) \times (F(4)!)) \\86365 &:= -((((F(8) + F(6)) + 3!) - (6! \times 5!)) \\86366 &:= -((((F((F(8) - 6))) - (3!^6)) - (F(6)!)) \\86373 &:= (8! + (F(F(6)) \times ((3^7) + 3!)) \\86374 &:= ((8 \times 6!) + (((F(3!))! - F(7)) \times F(F(4)))) \\86376 &:= (((8 \times 6!) - 3) + 7!) \times F(6) \\86379 &:= -((F(8) - (6! \times (((3 - 7) + 9)!)) \\86380 &:= (-F(8) - ((-6!) \times (-((3 - 8)!)) - 0!)) \\86384 &:= (8 \times ((6! - F(3)) + (8!/4))) \\86385 &:= (-((F(8) - 6)) - ((-((F(3) - 8)!)) \times (-5!)) \\86387 &:= ((8 \times 6!) + ((F(3) \times 8!) - F(7))) \\86392 &:= (8 \times ((6! \times (3! + 9)) - F(2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
86393 &:= ((-8) + ((6!^{F(3)}) - F(9)))/3! \\
86394 &:= (((8 \times 6!) \times (3! + 9)) - (F(4))!) \\
86398 &:= (((8! + 6!) - F(3)) + (9!/8)) \\
86400 &:= ((8! - (6! \times (-4))) \times (0! + 0!)) \\
86402 &:= ((8! - ((6! \times (-4)) - 0!)) \times 2) \\
86405 &:= (((8 \times 6!) \times F(4) + 0!) \times 5) \\
86406 &:= (((F(8) \times 6!) - ((F(4))!)!) + 0!) \times 6) \\
86412 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (F((F((F(4))!) + 1))^2)) \\
86413 &:= ((F(8) + (6! \times ((4 + 1))!)) - F(3!)) \\
86414 &:= ((8 + (6! \times ((4 + 1))!)) + (F(4))!) \\
86415 &:= (F(8) - ((6! - (F(4))!) \times (-1 - 5!))) \\
86416 &:= (8 + ((6! \times ((4 + 1))!) + F(6))) \\
86420 &:= (F(8) + ((6! \times ((F(4) + 2))!) - 0!)) \\
86421 &:= (F(8) + (6! \times (((4 + 2) - 1))!)) \\
86422 &:= (F(8) - ((-6!) \times ((F(4) + 2))!) - F(2)) \\
86423 &:= (F(8) - ((-6!) \times ((F(4) + 2))!) - F(3)) \\
86424 &:= (((8! - (6! \times (-4))) \times 2) + 4!) \\
86426 &:= (((8! - (6)) + F(4!)) - (2^{F(6)})) \\
86427 &:= ((F(8) + (6)) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-(-(2 - 7))!))) \\
86428 &:= (((-F(8)) \times (-F(6)) - (F(4))!)^2) - 8) \\
86433 &:= ((8! + (F(6))!) + ((F(4!)/F(3!)) - 3)) \\
86434 &:= (((8! - F(F(6))) + F(4!)) - F(F((3 + 4)))) \\
86435 &:= (((8 + (6! \times 4!)) - F(F(3))) \times 5) \\
86437 &:= (((8! - F(F(6))) + F(4!)) + 3) - F(F(7)) \\
86438 &:= (((8! + (6)) + F(4!)) - (F(3)^8)) \\
86440 &:= ((8 + (6! \times 4!)) \times (4 + 0!)) \\
86442 &:= ((F(8) + F(F(6))) + (((F(4))!)! \times ((F(4) + 2))!)) \\
86443 &:= ((F((8 + 6)) - (F(4))!) \times F(F((4 + 3)))) \\
86444 &:= ((8! - ((6!/F(4)) + (4))) + F(4!)) \\
86445 &:= (((8 \times 6!) + F(4)) \times F(4)) \times 5) \\
86447 &:= (((8! - (6)) + F(4!)) - F(F(4))) - F(F(7)) \\
86448 &:= ((8! - (6!/F(4))) + F((F(4) \times 8))) \\
86449 &:= (((8! - (6)) + F(4!)) - (F((4 + 9)))) \\
86453 &:= (((F(8) + F(6)) + 4!) - (-5! \times 3!)) \\
86454 &:= ((8! + (6)) + ((F(F(4)) \times (-5!)) + F(4!)))
\end{aligned}$$

- 86455** := ((8! – F(F((F(F(6))/F(4)))))) + F((5!/5)))
86456 := ((8!/6!) + ((4! × 5) × 6!))
86461 := (((8! + (6)) + F(4!)) – F(F((6 + 1))))
86463 := (((F(8) + (F(6)⁴)) × F(F(6))) + 3!)
86464 := ((F(F(8)) × F(6)) + (–(46) × 4!))
86465 := ((F(8) + ((6! × 4!) – F(6))) × 5)
86467 := (((((8! + (6)) + F(4!)) + 6) – F(F(7)))
86471 := (((F(F(8)) × F(6)) – ((F(4)!))!) – (F((F(7) + 1))))
86473 := (((((8! + F(F(6))) + F(4!)) – F(F(7))) – 3)
86474 := (((((8! + F(F(6))) – F(F(4))) – F(F(7))) + F(4!))
86475 := ((–(8) – ((6! × 4!) + (7))) × (–5))
86476 := (((8! + F(F(6))) + F(4!)) – (F((7 + 6))))
86480 := (8 × (F(F(F(6))) – (4 × F((8 + 0!))))
86484 := (8! + ((–(6) × F((F(F(F(4))) + 8))) + F(4!)))
86486 := (86 – ((–((F(4) – 8)))! × (–6!)))
86489 := –(((F((F(8) – F(6))) – F(4!)) – (8! + F(9))))
86493 := (((8! – (6)) + F(4!)) – (9 × F(F(3!))))
86494 := –((F(F(8)) + (((F(6)!)/(–4!)) × (F(9) + 4!))))
86496 := (8 × (((–(F(F(6))) × F((F(4)!)) + F(9)) + F(F(F(6))))))
86499 := ((–(F(8)) + (((F(6)! + F(4!))/9)) × 9)
86504 := (8 × ((F(F(F(6))) – 5!) – F((0! + (F(4)!))))
86505 := ((–(F(8)) – (6! × ((5 – 0!)!)) × (–5))
86512 := (8 × (F(F(F(6))) – (5! + 12)))
86513 := (F((F(8) – F(6))) + (5! × (–1 + 3!)))
86523 := (–((F(8) – (6! × 5!))) + F((2 × 3!)))
86524 := ((–(F(8)) – ((F(F(F(6))) – 5!) × (–2))) × 4)
86526 := ((F(8) × 6) – ((5!²) × (–6)))
86528 := (((((–(8) – F(6)) + 5!)²) × 8)
86533 := ((F(8) – F(6)) – (–(5!) × (F(F(3)) + 3!)))
86534 := (8 + ((F(F(6)) + (5!^{F(3)})) × (F(4)!))
86535 := (F(8) + (((6! × 5!) – 3!) + 5!))
86536 := ((–(8) + (6! × 5!)) + F((F(3) × 6)))
86537 := (((F(F(8)) – (F(6) + 5!)) × F(3!)) – 7)
86538 := (((F(8) × 6!) × 5) – F(3!)) + F(F(8)))
86541 := (F(8) + ((6! × 5!) + ((4 + 1)!))

$$\begin{aligned}86542 &:= (((8! + (6!/(-5))) + F(4!)) - 2) \\86543 &:= (((8! + (6!/(-5))) + F(4!)) - F(F(3))) \\86544 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(6) + 5!)) \times (4 + 4)) \\86545 &:= (F(8) + (((6! \times 5!) + (4)) + 5!)) \\86546 &:= (F(F(8)) - (F(F(6)) \times (-((5!/4!) \times 6!)))) \\86547 &:= -(((F(8) - (6! \times 5!)) - (4! \times 7))) \\86548 &:= (((F(8) \times 6!) \times 5) + F(F(4))) + F(F(8))) \\86549 &:= (8! + (((F(F(6)) \times (-5)) + F(4!)) - F(9))) \\86552 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (5! + (5 + 2)))) \\86553 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5!)) - F((5 \times F(3)))) \\86554 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5!)) - 54) \\86556 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((6! \times (-5)) + 5!)) \times 6) \\86559 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + (-5 - 5!)) - 9) \\86560 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 0 \\86561 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 1 \\86562 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 2 \\86563 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 3 \\86564 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 4 \\86565 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 5 \\86566 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 6 \\86567 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 7 \\86568 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 8 \\86569 &:= (F(F(8)) - 6 - 5!) \times F(6) + 9 \\86573 &:= (F(8) - ((F(F(F(6))) - ((5! + (7)))) \times (-F(3!)))) \\86574 &:= (((8! + (6)) - 5!) + F(((7 - F(4))))!) \\86577 &:= ((8 + (6! \times 5!)) + (F(7) \times F(7))) \\86580 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - F((-5) + F(8))) - 0!) \\86587 &:= (-F(8) - (F(6) \times (5! - F((8 + F(7)))))) \\86589 &:= (((8!/F(F(6))) \times 5) + (F(8))) \times 9 \\86593 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5!)) - (9 + 3!)) \\86594 &:= (((8! - F(6)) - 5!) + F(9)) + F(4!) \\86596 &:= ((-8) + (6! \times 5!)) - (F(9) \times (-6)) \\86600 &:= (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (((6 - 0!)! + 0!)))\end{aligned}$$

$$86604 := ((8 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 - 0!)!)) - 4)$$

$$86608 := ((F(F(8)) + (6!/(-6))) \times 08)$$

$$86614 := ((8 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - ((6 - 1)!)) + (F(4)!))$$

$$86616 := ((F(F(8)) - ((6!/6) - 1)) \times F(6))$$

$$86622 := ((8! - 66) + F(((2 + 2)!))$$

$$86624 := (8! - ((F(6) \times F(6)) - F(24)))$$

$$86625 := -(((F(8) - (6)) - ((6! + 2) \times 5!))$$

$$86632 := ((8 + 6!) \times ((6!/3!) - F(2)))$$

$$86633 := (F((F(8) - F(6))) + (((6!^{F(3)})/3!))$$

$$86634 := ((8! - (6 \times (6 + 3))) + F(4!))$$

$$86635 := ((-8!)/F(F(6))) - (F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3)))) \times (-5))$$

$$86637 := (-F((8 + F(6)))) - (-F(6) \times (F(F(F(3!))) + 7))$$

$$86640 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 0$$

$$86641 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 1$$

$$86642 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 2$$

$$86643 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 3$$

$$86644 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 4$$

$$86645 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 5$$

$$86646 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 6$$

$$86647 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 7$$

$$86648 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 8$$

$$86649 := 8! - 6 \times F(6) + F(4!) + 9$$

$$86652 := ((8! - (6 \times 6)) + F(((5 - F(2))))$$

$$86653 := (F(8) - ((F(6) + 6!) \times (-5!) + F(F(3))))$$

$$86654 := (((8! + (6)) + (F(6) \times (-5))) + F(4!))$$

$$86656 := (((8 - 6)^{F(6)}) + (5! \times 6!))$$

$$86659 := (((8! - F(F(6))) - F(6)) + F(-((5 - 9)!))$$

$$86664 := (((8! - F(6)) - F(6)) - F(6)) + F(4!))$$

$$86667 := (((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) \times F(6)) - ((6! + F(7))))$$

$$86672 := (8 \times ((F((F(6) + (6))) + (7!)) \times 2))$$

$$86673 := (((8! - F(F(6))) + 6) + F(((7 - 3)!))$$

$$86674 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(6) - 6!)) \times F(7)) - F(4!))$$

$$86676 := (((8!/6!) + (6)) \times F(F(7))) \times 6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86679 &:= ((8! + F(((F(6) \times F(F(6)))/7))) - 9) \\
 86682 &:= ((8! - (6)) + F(((6 \times 8)/2))) \\
 86684 &:= (F(((8 + F(6)) + F(6))) + ((8! - (4)))) \\
 86691 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (6!)) + F(-(((F(6) - F(9)) + 1)))) \\
 86694 &:= ((8! + (6)) + F((-6 + F(9)) - (4))) \\
 86696 &:= ((8! + F(6)) + F((F(6) \times (9 - 6)))) \\
 86699 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(6) + 6!)) + F((F(9) - 9))) \\
 86703 &:= (((8! + F(6)) + (7)) + F(((0! + 3)!)) \\
 86704 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((6! + F(7)))) + F((0! + 4!))) \\
 86709 &:= ((8! + F(F(6))) + F(((F(7) - 09)!)) \\
 86715 &:= (((F(8) + 6!) + 7!) \times 15) \\
 86722 &:= (((8! + F(F(6))) + F(7)) + F(((2 + 2)!)) \\
 86724 &:= ((8! + (-6) \times (-7) + F(2))) + F(4!) \\
 86728 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (7!/(-2 - 8))) \\
 86730 &:= ((8! + (6 \times 7)) + F(((3 + 0)!)) \\
 86733 &:= (((F(F(8)) - ((F(6) \times F(7)))) \times F(3!)) - 3) \\
 86734 &:= (((8 \times (6 + 7!)) - F(3)) + F(4!)) \\
 86735 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - F(F(7))) - 3!!) + 5! \\
 86736 &:= ((F(8) \times (F(6))^{7-3}) + 6!) \\
 86737 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(7))) - (3!! + 7)) \\
 86742 &:= (((8! + (F(6) \times 7)) + F(4!)) - 2) \\
 86743 &:= (((8! + (F(6) \times 7)) + F(4!)) - F(F(3))) \\
 86744 &:= (8! + (((F(6))!)/(((7 - 4)!)) + F(4!)) \\
 86746 &:= (((8 \times (F(6) + 7!)) + F(4!)) - 6) \\
 86752 &:= ((8 \times (F(6) + 7!)) + F(((5 - F(2))!)) \\
 86755 &:= ((8! + 67) + F((5!/5))) \\
 86756 &:= ((-F(8)) + F((F(F(6)) - 7))) + ((5! \times 6!)) \\
 86757 &:= ((F(8) - ((F(F(6)) + (7!)) \times 5!))/(-7) \\
 86764 &:= (((8! + F(F(6))) - F(F(7))) + (6^{F(4)!})) \\
 86767 &:= -((F(F(8)) - (((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) - (7!))) \\
 86769 &:= (((F(8) + 6!) \times F(7)) + F(6)) \times 9) \\
 86774 &:= (8! + (((F(F(6)) \times (-7)) + F(F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 86814 &:= (((F(8) \times 6) + 8!) + F(((1 \times 4)!)) \\
 86824 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (((8 - 2)! + 4!)) \\
 86826 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - ((F(8) + F(2)) + 6!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86832 &:= (8 \times (((6!/(-8)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 2)) \\
 86833 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (F(8))) - 3!!) + 3!) \\
 86834 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - 8) - 3!!) - (F(4)!) \\
 86835 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - 8) - 3!!) - (5) \\
 86837 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (-6 \times 8!)) + F((F(F(3!)) + 7))) \\
 86839 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - ((8 - F(3)))!) - 9) \\
 \\
 86840 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 0 \\
 86841 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 1 \\
 86842 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 2 \\
 86843 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 3 \\
 86844 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 4 \\
 86845 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 5 \\
 86846 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 6 \\
 86847 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 7 \\
 86848 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 8 \\
 86849 &:= -8 + F(6) \times F(F(8)) - F(4)!! + 9 \\
 \\
 86859 &:= (-(F(8)) - (-(F(6)) \times (F(F(8)) - (5! - F(9)))))) \\
 86861 &:= ((F(8) - 6!) - (-8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 1))) \\
 86863 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + (((F(8) - 6!) - 3!)) \\
 86864 &:= ((8 - 6!) \times ((F(8) \times (-6)) + (4))) \\
 86869 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + (F(8))) - ((-((6 - 9)))!)) \\
 86874 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(6)) \times 8) - (7!/F((F(4)!))) \\
 86876 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + (((F(8) + (7)) - 6!)) \\
 86894 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(6)) \times 8) - F((-9) + 4!)) \\
 86896 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 6) \times 8) - ((9 - 6)!)) \\
 86903 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + F((9 + 0!))) - 3!!) \\
 86918 &:= (((8!/6) - F(9)) \times F(-((1 - 8)))) \\
 86928 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (6!/(-9))) \times (F(2) \times 8)) \\
 86934 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (6!/(-9))) \times F(3!)) + (F(4)!)) \\
 86936 &:= (((8! - (6)) - F(9)) + (3!^6)) \\
 86938 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (((9 - F(3)))!/8)) \\
 \\
 86940 &:= (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 0 \\
 86941 &:= (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$86942 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 2$$

$$86943 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 3$$

$$86944 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 4$$

$$86945 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 5$$

$$86946 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 6$$

$$86947 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 7$$

$$86948 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 8$$

$$86949 := (-F(8) \times 6! + 9!)/4 + 9$$

$$86952 := (8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(9) + 5!)/2)))$$

$$86954 := -((F(F(8)) + (((6! \times F(9)) - (5)) \times (-4))))$$

$$86958 := ((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - F((9 + (-((5 - 8))!))))$$

$$86963 := ((8! + F(F(6))) - (F(9) - (6^{3!})))$$

$$86964 := (((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (F((9 + 6)))) + (F(4)!))$$

$$86973 := (((F(F(8)) - (6!)) \times 9) - (7!)) - F(F(3!))$$

$$86974 := -((F(F(8)) + ((6! \times F(9)) \times (-7 + F(4))))$$

$$86979 := ((F(F(8)) + F(-((F(6) - F(9)))))) + (7! \times (-9))$$

$$86994 := ((8! + ((F(6) \times F(9)) + F(9))) + F(4!))$$

$$87024 := ((F(F(8)) - (70 - 2)) \times F((F(4)!))$$

$$87044 := (((-F(8)) + F((F(7) + 0!))) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + F(4!))$$

$$87046 := ((8! + 70) + ((F(4)!)^6))$$

$$87048 := ((F(F(8)) - (F(7) \times (0! + (4)))) \times 8)$$

$$87064 := (((F((F(8) - (7))) - 0!) + (F(6)!)) + F(4!))$$

$$87087 := (((8!/(7 - 0!)) - F(8)) \times F(7))$$

$$87120 := ((((-8) + F(7))! + 1) \times ((2 + 0!)!))$$

$$87127 := (((8! \times F(7))/(1 + 2)! - F(F(7)))$$

$$87136 := (((F(F(8)) - F((F(7) - 1))) \times F(3!)) + (6!))$$

$$87144 := (((((-8) + F(7))! + 1) \times ((F(4)!))!)) + (4!))$$

$$87154 := (8! + ((F(F(7)) \times F(F(-((1 - 5)))))) + F(4!))$$

$$87183 := ((-8) - F((F(7) + 1))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(3!))$$

$$87184 := (8 \times (F(F((7 + 1)))) + (-8 \times (F(4)!))$$

$$87204 := (-((F(8) - (F(7) \times F(20)))) - ((F(4)!))!)$$

$$87230 := (F((8 + 7)) \times (F((2 \times 3!)) - 0!))$$

$$87232 := (8 \times (F(F((7 + F(2)))) - (F(F(3!)) \times 2)))$$

$$87233 := (8 + ((F(7) \times F((-F(2)) + F(F(3!)))) - (3!)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 87234 &:= (((F(8) \times F(7)) \times 2) + (F(3)!)) + F(4!)) \\ 87241 &:= ((((-8) + F(7)))! + F(2)) \times (((F(4)!))! + 1)) \\ 87242 &:= ((8 + F(F(7))) \times (2 - (((F(4)!))! / (-2)))) \\ 87246 &:= (F(8) + ((F(7) \times F((-F(2)) + F(F((F(4)!)))))) - (6!)) \\ 87247 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7) - 2)) \times F((F(4)!)) - F(F(7))) \\ 87248 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (((7 - 2)! / F(4))) \times 8) \\ 87256 &:= ((-8) \times F(7)) \times ((F(2) - 5!) - 6!) \\ 87264 &:= ((8! + (72 \times F(6))) + F(4!)) \\ 87266 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7!)) - ((-2) \times (F(6)!)) - (6!)) \\ 87296 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F((7 + 2))) \times F((9 - 6)!)) \\ 87303 &:= (-((F(8) \times F(7))) - ((F(F(F(3!))) + 0!) \times (-F(3!)))) \\ 87304 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F((7 + F(3)))) + 0!) \times F((F(4)!)) \\ 87306 &:= ((-F(8)) - F(F(7))) - (F(3!) \times (0! - F(F(F(6)))))) \\ 87314 &:= ((-F(8)) - F(F(7))) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-1) \times F((F(4)!))) \\ 87326 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - F((F(2) + F(6)))) \\ 87330 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - (30)) \\ 87333 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - ((3^3)) \\ 87334 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - F(3)) - 4! \\ 87336 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - (3 \times F(6))) \\ 87338 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) - 3!) / 3!) - F(8) \\ 87339 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - F(F(-(3 - 9)))) \\ 87340 &:= (-F(8)) - (((-F(7)) \times (F(3)!)) / (F(4)!)) - 0! \\ 87342 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 7) - F(F(3!))) \times F((F(4)!)) - 2) \\ 87343 &:= ((8 - F(F(7))) + (F(3!) \times F((4! - 3)))) \\ 87344 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - ((4 \times 4))) \\ 87345 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - (F(4) \times 5)) \\ 87346 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - (F(4)!)) - F(6) \\ 87347 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / F(3)) / F(4)) - F(7) \\ 87348 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - (4 + 8)) \\ 87349 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - F(F(4))) - 9 \\ 87353 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - (5)) - F(3) \\ 87354 &:= ((((-F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times (-3)) - 5!) \times (F(4)!)) \\ 87357 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F(3!)) - ((5! - F(7)))) \\ 87358 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - F(-(5 - 8))) \\ 87359 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) - 3!) / (F(-(5 - 9))))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87360 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 0 \\87361 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 1 \\87362 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 2 \\87363 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 3 \\87364 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 4 \\87365 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 5 \\87366 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 6 \\87367 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 7 \\87368 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 8 \\87369 &:= (-8 + F(7))! \times (F(3!) + 6!) + 9 \\ \\87372 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F(7)) - F(2) \\87373 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + (7)) + 3! \\87374 &:= (8! - (((F(F(7)) \times (-3)) + F(7)) - F(4!))) \\87379 &:= (F(F(8)) + (7 \times (F(F(F(3!)))) - (-7 + F(9)))) \\87380 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F(8)) - 0! \\87381 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F((8 \times 1))) \\87382 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F(8)) + F(2) \\87383 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F(8)) + F(3) \\87384 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + ((8 - 4)!)) \\87386 &:= (((8! + F(7)) \times F(3)) - (8!/(-6))) \\87389 &:= -(((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) - ((3! + F(F(8))) \times 9))) \\87391 &:= ((8 \times ((-F(7)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - 9) - 1) \\87392 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F(9)) - 2 \\87393 &:= (((8! \times F(7))/3!) + F(9)) - F(F(3)) \\87394 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) + (3! \times F(9)))/(F(4)!)) \\87395 &:= (((8! - F(7)) + 3!) + F(((9 - 5)!)) \\87408 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((7 \times F(4)) - 0!)) \times 8) \\87409 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4)!)) - F((0! + 9))) \\87413 &:= ((F(8) \times (-7)) - (F((F(4)!)) \times (1 - F(F(F(3!)))))) \\87414 &:= (((8! + (7)) + ((F(4)!))!) + (-1 + F(4!))) \\87415 &:= (((8! + (7)) + F(4!)) + (((1 + 5)!)) \\87416 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) - (F(4)!)) \times F((1 \times 6))) \\87418 &:= (((8! + F(7)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + (F((-1 + F(8))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87421 &:= (((8! + F(7)) + F(4!)) + (((2 + 1))!))! \\
 87423 &:= (((8! - F(F(7))) - F(F((4 \times 2)))) \times 3) \\
 87424 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / (F(4))!) + (2^{F(4)!})) \\
 87428 &:= (F(F(8)) - (7 \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - (F(2) + F(F(8)))))) \\
 87429 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (F(2) + F(9))) \\
 87430 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - F((F(3!) + 0!))) \\
 87431 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (-7 + 4!)) \times F(3!)) - 1) \\
 87432 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (-7 + 4!)) \times F((3 \times 2))) \\
 87433 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (-7 + 4!)) \times F(3!)) + F(F(3))) \\
 87434 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (-7 + 4!)) \times F(3!)) + F(F(4))) \\
 87435 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F(7) + F(4))) \times F(3!)) - (5)) \\
 87436 &:= (((F(8) + (7)) + F(4!)) + 3!!) + (F(6))! \\
 87437 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (F(3) + F(F(7)))) \\
 87438 &:= ((((-8) + F(7))! - F(F(4))) \times (3!! + (F(8)))) \\
 87439 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times F(3!)) - 9) \\
 \\
 87440 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 0 \\
 87441 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 1 \\
 87442 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 2 \\
 87443 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 3 \\
 87444 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 4 \\
 87445 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 5 \\
 87446 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 6 \\
 87447 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 7 \\
 87448 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 8 \\
 87449 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(7) - F(4)) \times F(F(4)!)) + 9 \\
 \\
 87452 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 7) \times F((F(4))!)) - (5!/2)) \\
 87453 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (5 + 3!)) \\
 87456 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(((7 - 4))!)) - ((5! - F(6)))) \\
 87458 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (-((5 - 8))!)) \\
 87462 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 7) - (F(4))!) \times F(6)) - 2) \\
 87463 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 7) - (F(4))!) \times F(6)) - F(F(3)) \\
 87465 &:= (-((8 + 7)) + ((F(4)^6) \times 5!)) \\
 87466 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (F(6) - (6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87467 &:= ((((-8) + F(7)))! \times (F(4)^6)) - F(7)) \\87470 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (7 - 0!)) \\87471 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (7 \times 1)) \\87473 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (7 + F(3))) \\87474 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (F(7) - F(4))) \\87477 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(((7 - 4)!)) + (-7) \times F(7)) \\87478 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (-7) + F(8)) \\87478 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + (-7) + F(8)) \\87484 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(((7 - 4)!)) - 84) \\87486 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / (F(4))! - (F(8) \times (-6))) \\87490 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(7)^{F(4)})) \times (9 + 0!)) \\87491 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 7) \times F((F(4))!)) - F((9 - 1))) \\87495 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 7) \times F((F(4))!)) - (9 + 5!)) \\87496 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) + (4! \times F(9))) / 6) \\87498 &:= (F(F(8)) + (7 \times ((4! - F(9)) + F(F(8)))) \\87504 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (F(7) - (5))) \times F((F(04))!)) \\87506 &:= (((F(F(8)) - 7) \times F((5 + 0!))) - 6) \\87520 &:= (8 \times (F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - ((2 + 0!)!)) \\87532 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (3!^2)) \\87533 &:= (F(8) - ((7 - F(F((5 + 3)))) \times F(3!)) \\87538 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (-5) \times 3!) + F(F(8))) \\87539 &:= (((((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (5)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(9)) \\87540 &:= (F(F(8)) - (7 \times ((5 - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 0!)) \\87542 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (4! + 2)) \\87543 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - (4!)) - F(F(3))) \\87544 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (7 - 5)) - (F(4))!) \times 4) \\87546 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (7 - 5)) \times F((F(4))!)) - 6) \\87549 &:= -((F(8) \times (F(7) - ((5! + F(4)) \times F(9)))) \\87552 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7 - 5)) \times F(((5 - 2)!)) \\87554 &:= (((8! \times (F(F(7)) - (5))) / 5!) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\87562 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) - ((6/2)!)) \\87574 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + ((7 - 4)!)) \\87583 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + (F(8) - 3!)) \\87584 &:= (((-8) + 7!) + 5!) \times (F(8) - (4)) \\87594 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (F(7) - (5))) + F(9)) - F((F(4))!))\end{aligned}$$

$$87602 := ((F(8) + F(7)) + (F(F(F(6)))) \times F(((0! + 2)!)))$$

$$87603 := (((F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6)) - F(F((03)!)))$$

$$87604 := ((F(8) + (7)) + ((F(F(F(6)))) + 0!) \times F((F(4)!)))$$

$$87609 := (F(F(8)) + ((7 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + 0!)) + F(9))$$

$$87625 := (((F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6)) + (F(2)^5!))$$

$$87630 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 0$$

$$87631 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 1$$

$$87632 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 2$$

$$87633 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 3$$

$$87634 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 4$$

$$87635 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 5$$

$$87636 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 6$$

$$87637 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 7$$

$$87638 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 8$$

$$87639 := (F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6) + 3! + 9$$

$$87640 := (((8! + F(F(7))) + (6!)) + F(4!)) - 0!$$

$$87641 := (((8! + F(F(7))) + (6!)) + F(((4 \times 1)!))$$

$$87642 := (((8! + F(F(7))) + (6!)) + F(4!)) + F(2)$$

$$87643 := (((8! + F(F(7))) + (6!)) + F(4!)) + F(3)$$

$$87644 := (((F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6)) + (4! - (4)))$$

$$87653 := (((F(F(8)) - 7) \times F(6)) + 5!) + F(F(3!))$$

$$87654 := (((F(F(8)) + 7) \times F(6)) + (5!/4))$$

$$87664 := (((F(F(8)) + (7 + F(6))) \times F(6)) - (4!))$$

$$87671 := (((F(F(8)) + F(7)) \times (F(6)!)/7!) - 1)$$

$$87675 := ((8 \times F((F(7) + F(6)))) - (F(7) - 5!))$$

$$87678 := (((F(8)/7)! + (F(6) \times (F(7) + F(F(8))))))$$

$$87694 := -(((F(F(8)) + (7!)) - (6! \times F((9 + F(4))))))$$

$$87695 := (-((F(F(8)) - 7)) + ((F(F(F(6)))) \times 9) + 5!))$$

$$87697 := (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((-((6 - 9)!))) + F(F(7)))$$

$$87704 := (8 \times ((-7) + F(F((7 + 0!)))) + (4!))$$

$$87723 := (((F(F(8)) - (7!)) \times F(7)) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))$$

$$87724 := (((F(F(8)) - (7!)) \times F(7)) + F(F((2 \times 4)))$$

$$87726 := (((F(F(8)) - (7!)) \times F(7)) + 2) + F(F(F(6)))$$

- 87733** := (((F(F(8)) + F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) × F(3!)) - 3
87734 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + (7))) × F(3!)) + (F(4)!))
87735 := ((8 - F(F(7))) - ((F(7) + 3!) × (-5!))
87737 := (((F(F(8)) - F((-7) + F(7)))) × F(3!)) + F(F(7))
87738 := (((F(8)/(-7)) + F((F(7) + 3!))) × F(8))
87743 := ((F(8) - 7!) - ((-F(7) - F(4!)) × F(3)))
87744 := (((F(F(8)) + F(F((-7) + F(7)))) × F((F(4)!)) + F((F(4)!))
87745 := ((F((F(8) - (7))) × F(F(7))) + (4! - 5!))
87747 := ((8 × (F(F(F((-7) + F(7)))))) + 4!) - F(7))
87748 := (((F(F(8)) - (7!)) × F(7)) + (4!)) + F(F(8))
87753 := ((F(F(8)) - F(F(7))) + (-((F(7) - 5!) × 3!))
87763 := (((8 + 7) × F(7)) + (F(F(F(6))) × F(3!))
87780 := (-F(8)) × ((F((F(7) + (7))) - F(F(8))) + 0!))
87783 := (8! + (F(7) × ((7 + F(F(8)))/3)))
87784 := ((F(F(8)) + ((-7) + F(7)) + F(8)) × F((F(4)!))
87793 := ((-8) + F(F(7))) - (F(-((F(7) - F(9)))) × (-F(3!)))
87794 := (-(((F(F(8)) + 7) - F(F(7)))) + (9 × F(F(F((F(4)!))))))
87798 := (8! + (((F(F(7)) + (7!)) × 9) + (F(8))))
87801 := (F(8) × F((((F(7) + 8) - 0!) - 1)))
87806 := (F(F(8)) + (7 × (F(F(8)) + F((0! + F(6))))))
87809 := ((8 + F(F(7))) - (F(F(8)) × (0! - 9)))
87814 := ((F(8) + F(F(7))) - (-((F(F(8)) - 1) × F((F(4)!)))
87824 := (8 × ((7 + F(F(8))) + (F(2) + 4!)))
87830 := ((F(8) + F(F(7))) - (-8 × (F(F(F(3!))) + 0!))
87832 := (-8) - (-F((7 + 8)) × F((3! × 2)))
87834 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(8))) × F(3!)) - (F(4)!))
87835 := (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(8))) × F(3!)) - (5))
87839 := (-((8 - 7)) - (-8 × (F(F(F(3!))) + F(9))))
87857 := (((F(F(8)) + 7) × F((8 - 5)!)) + F(F(7))
87864 := (((F(F(8)) + F(7)) × 8) + (F(6) × 4!))
87883 := ((F(8) × 7) - ((-F(8) - F(F(8))) × F(3!)))
87904 := ((F(F(8)) + ((7 + F(9)) + 0!)) × F((F(4)!))
87913 := (8! + (7 × (F(9) + F((-1 + F(F(3!))))))
87923 := (((F(F(8)) + (7!)) × (F(9) - F(2)))/3!)
87933 := (((F(F(8)) + (7 × 9)) - (F(3)!)) × (-3))

$$\begin{aligned}87938 &:= (8! + (((F(F(7)) + 9)^{F(3)}) - F(F(8)))) \\87940 &:= ((F(8) \times (7! - 9)) - F((F(F((F(4)!)) + 0!))) \\87942 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(7) + F(9))) \times F((F(4)!)) - 2) \\87943 &:= (87 - (-F(9)) \times F((4! - 3!))) \\87946 &:= (F(F(8)) - (7 \times ((-9) \times (F(4)!)) - F(F(F(6)))))) \\87953 &:= (8 - (-F(7)) \times F(((9 + 5) + 3!))) \\87955 &:= ((F(((8 \times 7) - F(9))) - 5!) \times 5) \\87963 &:= ((8! + F((7 + 9))) + (6^3)) \\87967 &:= ((87 + F(9)) \times (6! + (7))) \\87984 &:= (((F((F(8)/7)) + 9!) - F(F(8)))/4) \\88008 &:= ((F(F(8)) + F((8 + 0!) + 0!)) \times 8) \\88034 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) - (F(F((0! + 3!))) \times (-F(F(4)))))) \\88047 &:= (((8 \times (F(F(8)) - 0!)) + ((F(4)!))!) - F(F(7))) \\88048 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(8) - 0!) \times F(4))) \times 8) \\88049 &:= ((8 + F((F(8) - 0!))) \times (4 + 9)) \\88064 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) - 0!)) - (F(F(6)) \times (-4!))) \\88065 &:= (((-8) + F(8)) \times F((-0! + F(F(6)))) + 5!) \\88074 &:= (((F(8) \times (8 + 0!)) \times F(F(7))) \times F(F(4))) \\88083 &:= (((-8!) + F((8 - 0!))) + F(F(8))) \times (-3) \\88088 &:= (((8 \times 8) + 0!) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\88121 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) \times (1 + 2)) - 1) \\88122 &:= ((8! - F(F(8))) \times ((1^2) + 2)) \\88123 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) \times (1 + 2)) + F(F(3))) \\88124 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) \times (1 + 2)) + F(F(4))) \\88125 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) + 1) \times (-2 - 5)) \\88133 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) + 1) \times 3) + F(3!) \\88134 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((8! + (1 + 3)))) \times (-F(4))) \\88137 &:= ((8 - F((F(8) + 1))) + (F(F(3!)) \times 7!)) \\88143 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) - (1 - (4!^{F(3)}))) \\88144 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) + (((1 \times 4)! \times 4!)) \\88146 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) + 1) \times F(4)) + F(F(6)) \\88154 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) + (F(15) - 4!)) \\88166 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((F((8 - 1))!)/((F(6)! + (F(6)!)))) \\88173 &:= ((F(F(8)) - ((8! + (17)))) \times (-3)) \\88232 &:= (8 \times ((82 + F(F(F(3!)))) + F(2)))\end{aligned}$$

- 88233** := (((F(F(8)) × 8) − F((2 + F(3!)))) + (3!))
88234 := (((F(8) + F((F(8) − 2))) × F(F(3!))) − F((F(4))!))
88235 := ((−((8 × 8)) + F((F(2) + F(F(3!)))))) × 5
88236 := (((F(8) + F((F(8) − 2))) × F(F(3!))) − 6)
88237 := (((F(F(8)) + (82)) × F(3!)) + F(7))
88241 := (((F(8) + F((F(8) − 2))) × F(F((F(4))!))) − 1)
88243 := (((F(8) + F((F(8) − 2))) × F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F(3)))
88244 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((2 + 4!)^{F(F(4))}))
88245 := (((F(F(8)) − (8! + F(2))) × (−F(4))) + 5!)
88246 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((−2) × F(F((F(4))!))) + (6!))
88256 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + (−((2⁵)) + 6!))
88264 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((F(2) × 6!) − 4!))
88266 := (((F(F(8)) × 8) − F(2)) − F(F(6))) + (6!))
88268 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((F(2) + 6!) − F(8)))
88273 := (F(F(8)) − (((8! + 2) − (7^{3!}))))
88274 := ((F(F(8)) − (8! + F(2))) + (7^{F(4)!}))
88276 := (F(F(8)) − (((8! − F(2)) − ((7⁶))))
88278 := (8! + (F((8/2)) × (7! + F(F(8))))
88279 := (((F(F(8)) × 8) + (−((F(2) − 7))))!) − 9)
88280 := (8 × (F(F(8)) + F(((2 + 8) + 0!)))
88283 := (−F(8)) + (((F(F(8)) + 2) × 8) + 3!))
88284 := (((F(F(8)) × 8) + (−((2 − 8))))!) − 4)
88285 := ((8! − F((F(8) − F(2)))) − (F(F(8)) × (−5)))
88287 := (((F(F(8)) × 8) − F(2)) + (((F(8)/7))!))
88288 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((2 + (8/8))!))
88288 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((2 + (8/8))!))
88296 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) − (((F(2) − 9) − 6!))
88303 := ((8 × (F(F(8)) + F(3))) − (0! − 3!))
88304 := ((8 × (F(F(8)) + F(3))) + ((F(04))!))
88305 := (−F(8)) × (−F((F(8) − F(3)))) − (−((0! − 5)))!))
88307 := (((F(8) × (F(8) − 3)) + 0!) × F(F(7)))
88308 := (((F(F(8)) × 8) + 3!) − (0! − F(8)))
88309 := (((F(F(8)) × 8) + 3!) + F(−((0! − 9)))
88312 := ((8 × (F(F(8)) + 3)) + (((1 + 2))!))

$$\begin{aligned}88313 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 3)) - (-1 - 3!)) \\88324 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 8) + (3!^2)) + ((F(4))!)) \\88325 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((8!/3!) - F(2))) \times 5) \\88326 &:= (-F(8) \times (((-F(8) + 3!) + 2) \times (-6))) \\88330 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((8!/3!))) \times (3! - 0!)) \\88333 &:= (F(8) + (((F(F(8)) + 3) \times F(3!)) + 3!)) \\88334 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!)) + (3! - F(F(4)))) \\88335 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((8! + 3!)/3!)) \times 5) \\88337 &:= (((F(F(8)) - ((8! - 3!))) \times (-3)) + F(F(7))) \\88342 &:= ((-(((8) + F(8))^3)) + F(4!)) \times 2) \\88343 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 8) + 3!) + F((4 + 3!))) \\88344 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(3))) - (4! \times (-4)))) \\88345 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((8!/3!) + F(4))) \times 5) \\88346 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 8) \times F(3!)) - (F(4)!)) + (6!)) \\88347 &:= (-F(8) \times (((F(8) - 3!) \times (F(4)!)) - F(7))) \\88352 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 8) \times F(3!)) + (((5 - 2)!))!) \\88354 &:= (((F(F(8)) + ((8!/3!))) \times 5) + (4!)) \\88355 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((8!/3!) + (5))) \times 5) \\88360 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3!))) + ((6 - 0!))!)) \\88368 &:= (8! + ((F((8 \times 3))/6) + 8!)) \\88374 &:= ((-F(8) \times (F(F(8)) + (-3 \times 7!))) + ((F(4))!)) \\88376 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) \times 3) + F(F(7))) + F(F(6)) \\88384 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + ((3! \times F(8)) - 4!)) \\88392 &:= ((8! + 8!) - (-3 \times F((9 \times 2)))) \\88394 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) \times 3) - (-F(9) \times F((F(4)!))) \\88395 &:= ((F(8) \times (F((F(8) - F(3))) + F(9))) - 5!) \\88397 &:= (8 - (((F(8)^3) \times (-9)) - 7!)) \\88416 &:= ((8! + 8!) + ((F(4))!^{-1+6})) \\88423 &:= ((8! - F(F(8))) + (F(4))^{2+F(3!)})) \\88427 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 8) - F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 2))) + (7!)) \\88432 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) + (4! \times (3!^2))) \\88434 &:= ((-8!) - ((F(F(8)) \times (F(4)!)) \times (-3!)))/4) \\88435 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 8) + F((4^{F(3)}))) - 5!) \\88444 &:= (-((F(8) - (8!/F(4)))) + F((F(F(F(4))) + (4!))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}88448 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times (-8) + 4!)) - F(4!)) - 8!) \\88449 &:= ((-F(8)) \times (F(F(8)) - (4!))) + F(-(((F(4))! - F(9)))) \\88452 &:= ((F(8) + (8!/4!)) \times 52) \\88456 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(8))) \times (F(4) + (5))) + (6!)) \\88457 &:= ((8 \times ((F(F(8)) - F((F(4))!)) + 5!)) - 7) \\88464 &:= (((F(F(8)) + ((8 - F(4))!)) - F(6)) \times F((F(4))!)) \\88467 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + (4!))) + (6! - F(7))) \\88472 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) + (4!)) + F((F(7) - 2)))) \\88473 &:= (-F(8)) \times (-((8 \times 4) - F((F(7) + 3!)))) \\88475 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) \times F(4)) + F(F(7))) + 5! \\88485 &:= (F(8) - (8 \times (F((F(4))! - ((F(F(8)) + 5!)))))) \\88494 &:= (F(8) \times (F((F(8) - F(F(4)))) + (9 + 4!))) \\88496 &:= ((8 \times ((F(F(8)) - F((F(4))!)) + F(9))) + (6!)) \\88504 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (5! - F(04)))) \\88506 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) - (0! + F(F(6)))) \\88507 &:= (-F(8)) - ((F(F(8)) + 5!) \times (-0! + (7))) \\88508 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + (0! - F(8))) \\88512 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (5! - (1 \times 2)))) \\88513 &:= (-((F(8) + F(8))) + (5 \times F((1 + F(F(3!)))))) \\88514 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) - 14) \\88515 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + ((5! - 1)))) - (5)) \\88519 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) - (1 \times 9)) \\88520 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 0 \\88521 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 1 \\88522 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 2 \\88523 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 3 \\88524 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 4 \\88525 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 5 \\88526 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 6 \\88527 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 7 \\88528 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 8 \\88529 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5! - F(2)) + 9 \\88530 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 0\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}88531 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 1 \\88532 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 2 \\88533 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 3 \\88534 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 4 \\88535 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 5 \\88536 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 6 \\88537 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 7 \\88538 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 8 \\88539 &:= 8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(3) + 9 \\88541 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(((F(4))! + 1))) \\88542 &:= ((8 - F(8)) + (5 \times F((4! - 2)))) \\88543 &:= ((8 \times ((F(F(8)) + 5!) + F(F(4)))) - F(F(3))) \\88546 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + (4! - (6))) \\88547 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + ((F(4))! + F(7))) \\88548 &:= (((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(8))) \\88549 &:= (F(8) - (-((F(F(8)) + 5!)) \times F(-((F(4) - 9)))) \\88552 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (5! + (5 - 2)))) \\88553 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + (5^{F(3)})) \\88555 &:= (F((F(8) + ((8 \times (5 - 5))))!)) \times 5 \\88559 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) - (-5 - 5!))) - 9) \\88562 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + F((F(6) + F(2)))) \\88563 &:= ((F((8 + 8)) \times F((5 + 6))) + 3!!) \\88564 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + (6^{F(F(4))})) \\88568 &:= (-8) - ((F(F(8)) + ((5! + (6)))) \times (-8)) \\88575 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) - ((-5) + 7!)/(-5)) \\88576 &:= (-8) - ((F(F(8)) + ((5! + (7)))) \times (-F(6))) \\88577 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + (7 \times 7)) \\88583 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + F((8 + F(3)))) \\88584 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (5! + (F(8)/F(4)))) \\88586 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (8 + 5!)) \times 8) - 6) \\88592 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (8 + 5!)) \times (9 - F(2))) \\88594 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + (5! + 9))) - (F(4))!) \\88624 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (-6) \times (2 - 4!))) \\88644 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (F((8 + 6)))) \times 4) + F(4!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}88647 &:= ((-(F(8)) - (-((8! + 6!)/(F(4))!)) \times F(7)) \\88656 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((8 + F(6)) + 5!)) \times F(6)) \\88676 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(F(8))) - (F(6))!) \times (-7)) - (F(6))!) \\88680 &:= (8! + (8 \times (-6!) + F((F(8) - 0!)))) \\88704 &:= ((88 \times 7!)/(0! + (4))) \\88707 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(7) - 0!)))) - F(7)) \\88713 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(7)))) + (1 - 3!)) \\88714 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(7) - 1)))) - (F(4))!) \\88720 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + F((F(7) - ((2 \times 0)!)))) \\88725 &:= (F(8) - ((8! \times (F(7) - 2))/(-5))) \\88733 &:= (F(8) + (((F(F(8)) + F(F(7))) \times F(3!)) - 3!)) \\88737 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F(3!)) - 7) \\88738 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 8) + ((-F(7) \times 3!)/(-8))) \\88742 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - 2) \\88743 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(8) \times 7)) \times F((F(4))!)) - F(F(3))) \\88746 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (8!/((7 - 4)!)) \times F(F(6))) \\88754 &:= (((F(F(8)) \times 8) + (F(F(7)) \times 5)) + F(F((F(4))!))) \\88794 &:= (((8! - F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - 9) \times F(4)) \\88830 &:= (F((8 + 8)) \times (F((8 + 3)) + 0!)) \\88834 &:= ((-8) - ((8! - F(F(8))) \times (-3))) + ((F(4))!) \\88838 &:= (8 + ((-F((8 + 8))) \times 3!)/(-8)) \\88848 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (-8) \times F(8))) - F((F(4))!)) \times 8) \\88864 &:= (8 \times ((F(F(8)) + ((F(8) \times F(6)))) - (F(4))!)) \\88935 &:= ((F(8) + (F(8) \times F(9))) \times (F(F(3)) + 5!)) \\88936 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(8)) - 9)) + ((F(3) \times 6!)) \\88944 &:= (((F(F(8)) - (8! + F(9))) \times (-F(4))) + ((F(4))!) \\88949 &:= (((F(8) \times (8! + 9)) - F(4!))/9) \\88956 &:= ((-8) + (F(8) \times F(9))) \times (5! + (6)) \\88984 &:= (((8 \times F(8)) + 9) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4))!) \\89034 &:= ((-((F(8) + 9!)) + F((-0! + F(F(3!)))))/(-4)) \\89037 &:= ((F(F(8)) - F(9)) + (-((0! - 3!)^7)) \\89052 &:= -((F(F(8)) - ((9 + 0!)^5) - 2)) \\89053 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - ((9 + 0!)^5)) + F(F(3))) \\89054 &:= -((F(F(8)) - ((9 + 0!)^{5!/4!})) \\89088 &:= (((F(8) \times 9) + 0!) + F(F(8))) \times 8\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89088 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + (0! + (9 \times F(8)))))) \\
 89164 &:= ((F((8 + 9)) - 1) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F((F(4))!))) \\
 89167 &:= (-((F(7) \times (6! - 1))) + (9 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 89167 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 9) - ((-1 + 6!) \times F(7))) \\
 89187 &:= ((F(F(7)) - (8!/(1 \times 9))) \times (-F(8))) \\
 89246 &:= (8! + (F(9) \times (-F(2)) - (F(F(4)) \times (-6!)))) \\
 89248 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (((9 - 2)!/4!)) \times 8) \\
 89248 &:= (8 \times (((F(4))! \times (F(2) + F(9))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 89264 &:= (((8! + F((9 \times 2))) - F(6)) + F(4!)) \\
 89267 &:= -((F(7) - (((6! \times 2) \times F(9)) + 8!)) \\
 89267 &:= (8! - (((F(9) \times (-2)) \times 6!) + F(7))) \\
 89314 &:= (8! + (F(9) \times ((3!! + 1) + ((F(4))!))) \\
 89320 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (9 \times 3!!)) \times 20) \\
 89333 &:= (F((8 + 9)) - ((F(F(F(3!))) + (F(F(3!)))) \times (-F(3!)))) \\
 89334 &:= (-F(8)) \times (((9 + F(3)) - 3!!) \times (F(4))!) \\
 89344 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(9) + 3) \times (F(4))!)) \times F((F(4))!)) \\
 89345 &:= ((F((-8) + F(9))) + 3!!) - (F((F(4))!)^5) \\
 89346 &:= (((8!/F((9 + 3)))^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 89352 &:= (-8!) - (-9) \times (F(3!) + (5!^2)) \\
 89355 &:= ((F(8) \times (F(9) + 3)) \times (5! - 5)) \\
 89360 &:= (8 \times ((-9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F((F(6) - 0!)))) \\
 89364 &:= ((F(8) + ((F(9) - 3) \times 6!)) \times 4) \\
 89367 &:= (((8!/(-9)) \times (F(F(3)) - F(F(6)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 89368 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (F(9) \times 3!)) + F(F(6))) \times 8) \\
 89384 &:= ((F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) + (-3! + F(F(8)))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\
 89388 &:= (((F(8) + (F(F(8)))/(-F(3)))) \times (-9)) + 8! \\
 89397 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 9) \times F(F(3!))) - (9!/(-8))) \\
 89424 &:= (8! + ((F((9 \times F(4))) - 2)/4)) \\
 89431 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F((9 + 4))) \times F(3!)) - 1) \\
 89432 &:= (F((8 + 9)) \times (4! + 32)) \\
 89433 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F((9 + 4))) \times F(3!)) + F(F(3))) \\
 89434 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F((9 + 4))) \times F(3!)) + F(F(4))) \\
 89440 &:= (((8!/9) - F((F(4))!)) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!)) \\
 89464 &:= (((F(F(8)) + (9 \times 4!)) + F(F(6))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\
 89466 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 9) - (4! \times F((F(6) + (6))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89474 &:= (8 - (((9! + 4!) - 7!)/(-4))) \\
 89476 &:= (- (F(F(8))) + (- (9) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6))))))) \\
 89480 &:= (((8!/9) - (F(4))!) \times (F(8) - 0!)) \\
 89487 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4))!)) + (F(9) + F(8))) \\
 89487 &:= ((F(8) + F(9)) - (F((F(4))!) \times (- (F(F(8)) + F(F(7)))))) \\
 89488 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F((9 - F(4)))) + (8!/F(8))) \\
 89532 &:= (8! + (9 \times (- (5) - (F(F(F(3!)))/(-2)))) \\
 89542 &:= ((F((F(8) - (9 - 5))) - F(4!)) \times (-2)) \\
 89544 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(9) \times (5! - F(4)))))) \times (F(4))! \\
 89563 &:= ((F(8) \times 95) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(3!))) \\
 89584 &:= ((- (8) + (F(9) \times 5!)) \times (F(8) + F(F(F(4)))))) \\
 89586 &:= (- (F(8)) \times ((9 - ((- ((5 - 8))!))!) \times 6)) \\
 \\
 89600 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 0 \\
 89601 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 1 \\
 89602 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 2 \\
 89603 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 3 \\
 89604 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 4 \\
 89605 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 5 \\
 89606 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 6 \\
 89607 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 7 \\
 89608 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 8 \\
 89609 &:= 8!/9 \times (F(F(6)) - 0!) + 9 \\
 \\
 89623 &:= (- (8) - (- (9) \times (F(F(F(6))) - F((2 \times F(3!)))))) \\
 89624 &:= (((8!/9) + (F(6))!) \times 2) + (4!) \\
 89634 &:= (((F(8) \times (- (9) + 6!)) + F(3!)) \times (F(4))!) \\
 89642 &:= (((8!/9) + (F(6))!) + F(F((F(4))!))) \times 2 \\
 89704 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(9)) + F(F(7))) \times F((F(04))!)) \\
 89733 &:= (- (F(8)) \times ((F(9) + F(7)) - (3! \times 3!))) \\
 89734 &:= (8 + ((F(9) \times 7) \times F((F(3!) + (F(4))!)))) \\
 89737 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 9) + F(F(7))) \times F(3!)) + F(F(7)) \\
 89737 &:= (F(F(7)) + (F(3!) \times ((F(F(7)) + 9) + F(F(8)))) \\
 89740 &:= (((8!/9) + (7)) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) - 0!)) \\
 89744 &:= (8 \times (F(9) + (F(F(7)) \times (4! + 4!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89747 &:= (((-(7^4)) + 7!) \times F(9)) + F(8) \\
 89747 &:= (F(8) - (F(9) \times ((7^4) - 7!))) \\
 89754 &:= ((8! + ((9! + 7!)/5!)) + F(4!)) \\
 89767 &:= (((8 - (-9) \times F(7))) \times 6!) - F(F(7))) \\
 89767 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (6! \times ((F(7) \times 9) + 8)))) \\
 89783 &:= -((F(F(8)) - ((9! - 7) - (8^{3!})))) \\
 89785 &:= -((F(F(8)) + ((-9) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(8)))) - 5!)) \\
 89844 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - (9!/(8 + (F(4)!)))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 89845 &:= -(((F(F(8)) + 9) - ((8!/F(F(4))) \times 5))) \\
 89846 &:= -((F(F(8)) - (((9! + 8!)/4) - F(6))) \\
 89847 &:= -((F(F(8)) - (((9! + 8!)/4) - (7))) \\
 89848 &:= (((F(F(8)) + 9) \times 8) + (F(4!)/F(8))) \\
 89853 &:= (-F(8)) - (-9) \times (F(F(8)) + (-5! \times F(3!))) \\
 89854 &:= (-F(F(8))) + ((9! + (F(((8 - 5)!)))/4) \\
 89924 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(9)) + (-((9 - 2) \times (F((F(4)!))!)) \\
 89936 &:= ((8! \times (9 + F((F(9)/F(3)))))/6!) \\
 89937 &:= (((F(F(7)) + 3!) \times (-9)) + (9 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 89937 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 9) - (9 \times (3! + F(F(7)))) \\
 89938 &:= ((F((8 + 3!)) + 9) \times F((F(9) - F(8)))) \\
 89938 &:= (F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) \times (9 + F((3! + 8)))) \\
 89944 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (99 \times F(4))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 89964 &:= (((F(8) \times 9!) \times F(9))/6!)/4) \\
 89987 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(9)) + ((9 - 8!) \times 7)) \\
 90342 &:= (9 \times ((-(((0! + 3)!)) + F(F((F(4)!)))) \times (-2))) \\
 90343 &:= ((9!/(0! + 3)) - F(((F(4)! + F(3!)))) \\
 90354 &:= (((F(9) - 0!) + 3!) \times 5!) - (F(4)! \\
 90355 &:= (((F(9) - 0!) + 3!) \times 5!) - (5) \\
 90360 &:= (((F(9) - 0!) + 3!) \times ((6 - 0)!)) \\
 90434 &:= (((F(9) + 0!) \times F((4! - 3!))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 90435 &:= (((F(9) + 0!) \times F((4! - 3!))) - (5)) \\
 \\
 90440 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 0 \\
 90441 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 1 \\
 90442 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 2 \\
 90443 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 90444 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 4 \\
 90445 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 5 \\
 90446 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 6 \\
 90447 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 7 \\
 90448 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 8 \\
 90449 &:= (F(9) + 0!) \times F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 9 \\
 \\
 90464 &:= (((F(9) + 0!) \times F((4! - (6)))) + (4!)) \\
 90475 &:= ((F(9) + 0!) \times (F(F(F(4))) + F((F(7) + (5)))))) \\
 90477 &:= (9 \times (- (0!) + (F(F(4)) \times (7! - F(7)))))) \\
 90487 &:= ((9! / ((0 - 4) + 8)) - F(F(7))) \\
 90508 &:= ((F(9) \times (0! + 5!)) \times (0! + F(8))) \\
 90534 &:= (((- (9!) + (- ((0! - (5))))))! + (3!!)) / (-4) \\
 90543 &:= (((9! - ((0! + (5))))!) / 4) + 3 \\
 90544 &:= (((9! - ((0! + (5))))!) / 4) + 4 \\
 90573 &:= (((F(9) \times (05)!) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 90576 &:= ((90/5) \times (7! - F(6))) \\
 90578 &:= (F((9 \times F(-((0! - (5)))))) - ((7! \times F(8)))) \\
 90584 &:= ((F((9 + 05)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\
 90639 &:= (9 \times (((0! + (6)))! \times F(3)) - 9) \\
 90648 &:= (9 \times (((0 - (F(6)!)) / (-4)) - 8)) \\
 90665 &:= -((F((9 + 0!)) + (6! \times (- (6) - 5!)))) \\
 90666 &:= ((- (9) + (F(F(06)) \times 6!)) \times 6) \\
 90678 &:= (F(9) \times (((- ((0! - (6))))!) + 7) \times F(8)) \\
 90684 &:= (- (F(9)) - (((0! + F(6))!) - 8) / (-4)) \\
 90686 &:= -((F(9) + (((0 - 6!) \times F(8)) \times 6)) \\
 90694 &:= -(((F(9) - F(06)) + (9! / (-4)))) \\
 90704 &:= (((- (9) \times (0! - 7!)) + 0!) \times F(F(4))) \\
 90730 &:= ((9 \times (0! + (7! \times F(3)))) + 0!) \\
 90733 &:= (F(9) + ((- ((0! - 7!)) - 3!!) \times F(F(3!)))) \\
 90734 &:= (((9! + 0!) + F((7 + 3))) / 4) \\
 90736 &:= (F(9) + ((0! - 7!) \times (- (3 \times 6)))) \\
 90737 &:= (((F(9) \times (0! + 7!)) / F(3)) + 7!) \\
 90741 &:= (F((9 - 0!)) \times ((7! - ((F(4)!))!) + 1)) \\
 90742 &:= (((9 \times (0! + 7!)) + F(F(4))) \times 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 90743 &:= (((9! + 0!) + (7))/4) + F(F(3!)) \\
 90744 &:= ((9!/((0 \times 7) + 4)) + 4!) \\
 90746 &:= (((9 \times (0! + 7!)) \times F(F(4))) + F(6)) \\
 90747 &:= (9 \times (((0! + 7!) \times F(4)) - 7!)) \\
 90748 &:= (((9! + F(-((0! - F(7))))))/4) - 8) \\
 90754 &:= (F(9) - (((0! + F(7)) - (5)))! / (-4)) \\
 90762 &:= (F((9 - 0!)) \times ((7! - 6!) + 2)) \\
 90765 &:= (9 \times (((0! + F(7)) \times 6!) + (5))) \\
 90774 &:= (9 \times (((07!) + 7!) + (F(4)!)) \\
 90775 &:= (F((9 + 0!)) + (7! \times (F(7) + (5)))) \\
 90783 &:= (((9!/(0! - F(7))) - F(8)) \times (-3)) \\
 90784 &:= ((F(9) \times (0 - 7!)) + (8^{F(4)!})) \\
 90837 &:= (9 \times (F(-((0! - 8))) + ((F(3) \times 7!))) \\
 90845 &:= (((9! - 0!) + F(8))/4) + 5! \\
 90846 &:= ((F((9 - 0!)) + (F(8) \times ((F(4)!))) \times 6) \\
 90864 &:= (9 \times (((-((0! - 8)))! + F(6)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 90866 &:= (((((9 - 0!))! + F(F(8))) - (6!)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 90873 &:= (9 \times (0! - ((-8) - 7!) \times F(3))) \\
 90934 &:= (F(9) - (((09)! + 3!) / (-4)) \\
 90954 &:= (9 \times (F(F(-((0! - 9)))) + (-5! - ((F(4)!)))) \\
 91133 &:= (((F(9) + 11)^3) + F(3!)) \\
 91143 &:= ((F(9) + F(11)) \times (((F(4)!))! + F(F(3!)))) \\
 91344 &:= ((-F(9)) \times ((1 + 3!)!) + (4! \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 91358 &:= (F(9) \times (-1 + ((F(3!) + 5!) \times F(8))) \\
 91364 &:= (((F(9) + F(((1 + 3)!)) - (6!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 91377 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)))) - F(F(7)))) - (7!)) \\
 91434 &:= (((9!/(1 \times 4)) + 3!) - (F(4)!)) \\
 91437 &:= ((9! + F(((1 \times 4)!)) - F((F(F(3!)) + 7))) \\
 \\
 91440 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 0 \\
 91441 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 1 \\
 91442 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 2 \\
 91443 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 3 \\
 91444 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 4 \\
 91445 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 91446 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 6 \\
 91447 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 7 \\
 91448 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 8 \\
 91449 &:= 9!/(1 \times 4) + F(4)!! + 9 \\
 \\
 91464 &:= (((9!/(1 \times 4)) + 6!) + 4!) \\
 91474 &:= (F(9) - (-((((1 + 4))! + (7))) \times ((F(4))!))) \\
 91475 &:= ((F(9) + 1) - (((F(4))!) \times (- (7) - 5!))) \\
 91586 &:= (F(F((9 - 1))) + ((5! - 8) \times 6!)) \\
 91628 &:= (((-(((9 - 1))!) - F(F(6))) \times (-2)) + F(F(8))) \\
 91644 &:= ((-((91 \times 6)) + F(4!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 91648 &:= ((F(9) \times (-((1 - 6)))!) + (F((F(4))!) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 91674 &:= ((9 \times (-((1 \times 6)) + 7!)) + F(4!)) \\
 91694 &:= (((9!/F((1 \times 6))) - F(9)) + F(4!)) \\
 91734 &:= (((9!/(1 + 7)) + 3!) + F(4!)) \\
 91737 &:= ((9 \times (1 + 7!)) + F(-((3 - 7)))!) \\
 91743 &:= (((9 \times (1 + 7!)) + F(4!)) + 3!) \\
 91744 &:= ((9! + ((1 + 7)^4))/4) \\
 91747 &:= (((9! + ((1 \times 7))!)/4) - F(F(7))) \\
 91749 &:= (-F(((F(9) - 1) - F(7)))) + (F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)) \\
 91836 &:= (9 \times (((-1 + F(F(8))) - 3!!) - F(F(6)))) \\
 91943 &:= (-91) - (9 \times (((F(4))!)! - F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 91944 &:= (9 \times ((-((1 + 9)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (((F(4))!)!))) \\
 92032 &:= ((9 \times (-(((2 + 0))!)! + F(F(F(3!)))))) - 2) \\
 92033 &:= ((9 \times (-(((2 + 0))!)! + F(F(F(3!)))))) - F(F(3)) \\
 92034 &:= (9 \times (F(F((2^03))) - ((F(4))!))) \\
 92043 &:= (9 \times ((F(2) - ((F(04))!)! + F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 92047 &:= ((9 \times (-(((2 + 0))!)! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) + F(7) \\
 92267 &:= ((-9) \times (((F((2 + 2))!)! - F(F(F(6)))))) + F(F(7)) \\
 92304 &:= (F(9) - (2 \times (F(F((3! + 0!))) - F(4!)))) \\
 92317 &:= (((9!/2)/F(3)) + F(17)) \\
 92344 &:= (F(9) \times (((2 + F(F(F(3!))))/4) - F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 92349 &:= (((F(9) + F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (((F(4))!)!)) \times 9 \\
 92364 &:= ((9 + ((2 + 3))!) \times (6! - 4)) \\
 92394 &:= (9 \times (((-F(2)) + F(F(3!))) \times (-F(9))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92424 &:= (-((F((9-2)) \times 4!)) - (-2) \times F(4!)) \\ 92434 &:= (F(9) - (2 \times ((F((F(4)))! \times F(F(3!))) - F(4!)))) \\ 92437 &:= (((F(9) - F(2)) - F(4!)) \times (-F(3))) - F(F(7))) \\ 92439 &:= ((-F((9+2))) + F((4! + 3!)))/9 \\ 92442 &:= (((-((9-2)) \times F(F((F(4)))!)) + F(4!)) \times 2) \\ 92445 &:= (-9) - (2 \times (F(F((F(4)))!) - (F(4!) - 5!))) \\ 92446 &:= ((-F(9)) - (-2) \times F(4!)) - (F(F(4))^{F(6)}) \\ 92448 &:= (((9! \times (-2)) - (4!^{F(4)}))/(-8)) \\ 92454 &:= (-F(9)) - (2 \times ((4 + 5!) - F(4!))) \\ 92456 &:= (-F(9)) - ((-2) \times (F(4!) - 5!) + 6) \\ 92457 &:= (9 - (-2) \times (F(4!) - F((5+7)))) \\ 92462 &:= (-F(9)) - (-2) \times (F(4!) - ((6 - F(2)))!) \\ 92464 &:= ((-F(9)) - ((-2) \times F(4!))/F(6)) \times F((F(4))) \\ 92466 &:= ((9 \times (-2) + (F(4!)/F(6))) + (F(6))) \\ 92469 &:= ((-F(9)) - (-2) \times F(4!)) - F(-((F(F(6)) - F(9)))) \\ 92470 &:= (-F(9)) - (((-2) \times F(4!)) + F(F(7)) - 0!) \\ 92473 &:= (-9) - ((-2) \times (F(4!) + F(F(7)))) + 3!! \\ 92476 &:= (F(9) + (2 \times (F(4!) - (7 \times F(F(6)))))) \\ 92484 &:= (((9 - F(2)))! + ((F(4!)/8) + F(4!))) \\ 92487 &:= (-9) - (-2) \times (F(4!) - ((-8) + F(7)))! \\ 92494 &:= (-9) - ((-2) \times F(4!)) + F((9+4)) \\ 92498 &:= (F(9) - ((-2) \times F(4!)) + (F(9) \times 8)) \\ 92503 &:= (-F(F((9-2))) - (F(((5-0!)!) \times (-F(3)))) \\ 92505 &:= (9 + (2 \times (F(((5-0!)!) - 5!))) \\ 92524 &:= ((-92) - 5!) - (-2) \times F(4!) \\ 92530 &:= (F(9) + (2 \times (-5!) + F(((3+0!)!))) \\ 92534 &:= (F(9) - (2 \times ((5! - F(3)) - F(4!))) \\ 92537 &:= (F(9) - ((-2) \times F(((5 - F(F(3)))!)) + F(F(7))) \\ 92542 &:= ((-((92+5)) + F(4!)) \times 2) \\ 92544 &:= (((F(9)^2) \times 5!) + F(4!))/F(F(4)) \\ 92546 &:= (F(9) - (2 \times ((5! - F(4!)) - F(6))) \\ 92547 &:= (F(9) - ((2 \times (-5) - F(4!)) + F(F(7)))) \\ 92552 &:= ((-92) + F((5!/5))) \times 2 \\ 92568 &:= (((9-2))! - ((-5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92607 &:= (((9 - F(2)) \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((0! - 7!))) \\ 92608 &:= (((9 - 2)! - (-F(6) \times F(F(08)))) \\ 92616 &:= (((9 - 2)! - ((F(F(F(6))) + 1) \times (-F(6)))) \\ 92624 &:= (((9 - 2)! + ((F(F(F(6))) + 2) \times F((F(4)!)))) \\ 92625 &:= (9 - ((-2) \times F(((6 - 2)!)) + 5!)) \\ 92634 &:= (((F(9)/2) \times (-6)) + (F(3) \times F(4!))) \\ 92642 &:= (((-F(9)) - F((F(2) + (6)))) + F(4!)) \times 2 \\ 92643 &:= (-9) - ((2 \times F(F(6))) - F(4!)) \times F(3)) \\ 92644 &:= ((-92) + F((6 \times 4))) + F(4!) \\ 92647 &:= (-F(9)) + ((-2) \times (F(F(6)) - F(4!))) - F(7)) \\ 92648 &:= (-F(9)) + (2 \times ((-6) + F(4!)) - (F(8)))) \\ 92668 &:= ((F(9) - F((-((2 - 6))))!) \times (6 - 8)) \\ 92674 &:= (-F(9)) - (2 \times ((F(F(6)) - 7) - F(4!))) \\ 92694 &:= (((F(F((9 - F(2)))) \times (-F(F(6)))) + 9!) - (F((F(4)!)))! \\ 92702 &:= (-F(9)) + (2 \times F(((F(7) - 0!) \times 2))) \\ 92704 &:= (-F(9)) - (2 \times (-((7 \times 0)!) - F(4!))) \\ 92713 &:= (-9) - (2 \times (7 - F(((1 + 3)!))) \\ 92714 &:= (-F(9)) - (2 \times (-((7 - 1)) - F(4!))) \\ 92724 &:= ((9 - F((F(2) + (7)))) - (-2) \times F(4!)) \\ 92728 &:= ((F(((9 + 2) - 7)!) \times 2) - 8) \\ 92731 &:= (9 - (2 \times (7 - F(((3 + 1)!)))) \\ 92732 &:= ((F(((9 + 2) - 7)!) - F(3)) \times 2) \\ 92733 &:= ((F(((9 + 2) - 7)!) \times F(3)) - 3) \\ 92734 &:= (((9! \times 2)/7) - F((-3) + 4!)) \\ 92735 &:= (9 - (-2) \times (F(((7 - 3)!) - (5)))) \\ 92736 &:= ((92 \times 7!)/(-3) + F(6)) \\ 92738 &:= (((9! \times 2)/(-7)) + F((3! + F(8)))) \\ 92740 &:= (-9) - ((2 \times (-7) - F(4!)) + 0!) \\ 92741 &:= (-9) - (2 \times (-7) - F(((4 \times 1)!))) \\ 92742 &:= ((F(((9 + 2) - 7)) + F(4!)) \times 2) \\ 92743 &:= (9 - (((F(2)^7!) - F(4!)) \times F(3))) \\ 92744 &:= (((9! + (2^{F(7)}))/4) - 4!) \\ 92747 &:= (((9! \times 2)/7) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(7)) \\ 92748 &:= (F(9) - ((2 \times (7 - F(4!))) + 8)) \\ 92749 &:= (9 - (2 \times ((7 - F(4!)) - 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92753 &:= (- (9) - (2 \times (- (F(7)) - F(((5 - F(F(3))))!)))) \\ 92759 &:= (9 - (2 \times (- (7) - F(- ((5 - 9))!))) \\ 92768 &:= (F(9) + ((F(- ((F(2) - F(7)))) \times 6!) - F(F(8)))) \\ 92784 &:= (F(9) - (2 \times (- (7) - F(((8 - 4))!)))) \\ 92794 &:= (F(9) - ((- (2) \times F(((F(7) - 9))!)) - (4!))) \\ 92804 &:= ((F(9) + F((2 + F(8) + 0!))) \times F(F(4))) \\ 92814 &:= (F(9) - (2 \times (- ((F(8) + 1)) - F(4!)))) \\ 92817 &:= (9 \times ((2 \times ((8 - 1))!) + F(F(7)))) \\ 92824 &:= (((9 + 2) \times 8) - (- (2) \times F(4!))) \\ 92842 &:= (((F(9) - 2) + F(8)) + F(4!)) \times 2 \\ 92844 &:= ((- ((9 \times (2 - 8))) + F(4!)) \times F(F(4))) \\ 93015 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (0! + F(15)))) \\ 93024 &:= ((- (9) \times F((3! \times (0! + 2)))) \times (- 4)) \\ 93032 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!)) + (F(F(F(3!))) / (- 2))) \\ 93033 &:= ((9 + F(((3 + 0!))!)) + (3!^{3!})) \\ 93034 &:= (((- (F(9)) \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 0!)) - 3!) / (- 4)) \\ 93037 &:= (((- (F(9)) - F(((3 + 0!))!)) \times (- F(3))) + F(F(7))) \\ 93040 &:= (((- (F(9)) \times F(F(F(3!)))) / (0 - 4)) - 0!) \\ 93041 &:= ((- (F(9)) \times F(F(F(3!)))) / ((0 - 4) \times 1)) \\ 93042 &:= ((F(9) \times (F(3!) + 0!)) - (F(4!) \times (- 2))) \\ 93043 &:= (((- (F(9)) \times F(F(F(3!)))) / (0 - 4)) + F(3)) \\ 93044 &:= (((F(9) + ((3! - 0!))!) + F(4!)) \times F(F(4))) \\ 93048 &:= (((- (F(9)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (0! - ((F(4))!))!) \times 8) \\ 93056 &:= (((- (F(9)) + 3!!) + F(F(F((0! + (5)))))) \times F(6)) \\ 93064 &:= ((((- (F(9)) + 3!!) + 0!) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F((F(4))!)) \\ 93142 &:= (((F(9) \times 3!) - 1) + F(4!)) \times 2 \\ 93144 &:= (((F(9) \times 3!) + F(((1 \times 4))!)) \times F(F(4))) \\ 93156 &:= ((- (9) + F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) + ((5! \times 6!))) \\ 93165 &:= (F((F(F((9 - 3))) - 1)) + ((6! \times 5!))) \\ 93194 &:= (F(9) \times (- ((3!! - (F(19)))) - ((F(4))!))!) \\ 93234 &:= ((9! / 3!!) + (2 \times (- (3) + F(4!)))) \\ 93238 &:= ((9! / (F(3!)^2)) + (F(3!) \times F(F(8)))) \\ 93240 &:= 9! / 3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 0 \\ 93241 &:= 9! / 3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93242 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 2 \\93243 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 3 \\93244 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 4 \\93245 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 5 \\93246 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 6 \\93247 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 7 \\93248 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 8 \\93249 &:= 9!/3!! + 2 \times F(4!) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93256 &:= (((-9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (((F(2) + (5))))!) \times F(6)) \\93264 &:= ((((-9) + 3!!) + F(2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\93266 &:= (((-F(9)) + 3!!) \times (-((F(2) - (6))))!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\93267 &:= ((-9) \times ((F(F(3!)) + 2) - F(F(F(6)))) - (7!)) \\93274 &:= ((9 \times F(3!)) + (2 \times (F(F(7)) + F(4!)))) \\93284 &:= (-F(9)) + (((F(3!))! / (-2)) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(4)) \\93286 &:= (-F(9)) - (((3!! - F(2)) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(6))) \\93288 &:= (((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(2) + F(F(8)))) \times 8) \\93294 &:= (-F(9)) + ((3!! + F(F(-((F(2) - 9)))))) \times F((F(4)!))) \\93296 &:= (((F(9) \times F(3)) \times (-2)) \times (F(9) - 6!)) \\93303 &:= (-9) + ((3!^{3!}) \times F(03)) \\93304 &:= (F((9 - 3)) \times ((F(3!))! - F(-((0! - 4!)))) \\93314 &:= (((9 - 3)^{3!}) + 1) \times F(F(4)) \\93318 &:= ((9!/3!) + (3 \times F(F((1 \times 8)))) \\93319 &:= (-9) - (F(3!) \times (-3!!) - F(F(-((1 - 9)))))) \\93320 &:= (9 + (((3!^{3!}) \times 2) - 0!)) \\93322 &:= (9 + (((3!^{3!}) \times 2) + F(2))) \\93323 &:= (9 + (((3!^{3!}) \times 2) + F(3))) \\93324 &:= (9 + (((3!^{3!}) \times 2) + F(4))) \\93328 &:= (F((9 - 3)) \times (3!! + F((F(2) \times F(8))))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93330 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 0 \\93331 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 1 \\93332 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 2 \\93333 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 3 \\93334 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 4\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93335 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 5 \\93336 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 6 \\93337 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 7 \\93338 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 8 \\93339 &:= (9 + 3!^{3!}) \times F(3) + 9 \\93342 &:= ((-9) + ((3!^{3!}) + 4!)) \times 2 \\93343 &:= (F(9) - ((-((3!^{3!})) \times F(F(4))) + 3)) \\93344 &:= (((F((9 + 3!)) - F(3)) + F(4!)) + F(4!)) \\93345 &:= ((9^3) - ((-F(3)) \times F(4!)) + 5!) \\93346 &:= (F(9) + ((3!^{3!}) \times (-4 - 6))) \\93347 &:= (((F(9)/F(3))^3) \times ((F(4)! + F(7))) \\93348 &:= ((9 \times F(3)) \times ((-3!!) \times F((F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))) \\93357 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((3 - 5!) - 7!)) \\93361 &:= (F(9) - ((F(3!) \times (-3!!) - F(F(F(6)))) + 1)) \\93362 &:= (F(9) + (((3!^{3!}) + F(6)) \times 2)) \\93363 &:= (9 + ((-((3!^{3!})) - F(F(6))) \times (-F(3)))) \\93364 &:= (F(9) \times (F(3) + ((3! + F(6))^{F(4)})) \\93366 &:= ((9 \times 3!) + (F(3) \times (6^6))) \\93367 &:= (((F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (3!!)) \times F(6) - F(F(7))) \\93368 &:= ((F(9) + 3!) + (F(3!) \times (6! + F(F(8)))) \\93369 &:= ((9 - 3!!) - (F(F(3!)) \times ((F(6)!/(-9)))) \\93372 &:= (F(9) + (((3!^{3!}) + F(7)) \times 2)) \\93373 &:= ((F(9) \times (3! - 3!!)) + ((7^{3!})) \\93374 &:= (-F(9)) - (((F(3!)!)/3!) \times (-7)) - F(4!)) \\93375 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F(3!)) - (7! + 5!)) \\93383 &:= (-9) + (((F(3!) + 3!!) + F(F(8))) \times F(3!)) \\93384 &:= (((9^3) - F(3)) + F(F(8))) \times F((F(4)!)) \\93386 &:= (F(9) - ((3 + 3!!) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(6))) \\93387 &:= (((9 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (3!!)) \times 8) - F(7) \\93388 &:= ((-9!) + (F(3!)!) - (-38) \times F(F(8))) \\93394 &:= (F(9) + (((F(3!)! \times F(F(3!)))/9) - ((F(4)!)!)) \\93408 &:= (((-9) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (((F(4)!)! + 0!)) \times (-8)) \\93421 &:= ((-F(9)) + 3!!) - ((F(4!) \times (-2)) + 1) \\93422 &:= (((-F(9)) + 3!!) + F(4!)) + F(((2 + 2)!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93423 &:= (-F(9)) + (((F(3) \times F(4!)) + F(2)) + 3!!) \\
 93424 &:= ((((-F(9)) + 3!!) + F(4!)) + 2) + F(4!) \\
 93426 &:= (((9 + 3!) - F(4!)) \times (-2)) + (6!) \\
 93433 &:= (F(F((9 - F(3)))) \times (4! + F((3! + F(3!)))) \\
 93434 &:= ((-F(9)) + 3!!) + ((F(4!) + 3!) \times F(F(4))) \\
 93436 &:= (((9 + F(F(3))) - F(4!)) \times (-F(3))) + (6!) \\
 93437 &:= ((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) - ((F(4!) \times (-F(3))) + F(7))) \\
 93438 &:= (((9! + 3!!) / (F(4)!)) + (3 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 93442 &:= ((F(9) + 3!!) - ((4! - F(4!)) \times 2)) \\
 93443 &:= (-9) + (((F(3) \times F(4!)) - 4) + 3!!) \\
 93444 &:= ((((-9) + 3!!) - F(4)) + F(4!)) + F(4!) \\
 93445 &:= ((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) + ((F(4!) + F(4!)) - (5))) \\
 93446 &:= ((((-9) - F(F(3))) + F(4!)) + F(4!)) + (6!) \\
 93447 &:= ((-9) + 3!!) + (F(4!) \times F(-((4 - 7)))) \\
 93448 &:= ((F(9)^3) + ((4!^{F(4)} + 8!)) \\
 93449 &:= (((9! + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(4)!)/4) - 9) \\
 93450 &:= (((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) + F(4!)) + F(((5 - 0)!))!) \\
 93453 &:= (((F((9 - 3)))! + F(4!)) + F((5!/3!))) \\
 93454 &:= (((9! + F(F(F(3!)))) / (-F(F(4)))) + (5)) / (-F(F(4))) \\
 93456 &:= ((F((9/3)) \times F(4!)) - (5! \times (-6))) \\
 93457 &:= (F((F(9) - F(3!))) - (-4!) + (5! \times F(F(7)))) \\
 93462 &:= ((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) + ((F(4!) + 6) \times 2)) \\
 93463 &:= (9 - ((-F(3)) \times F(4!)) - (6! - F(3))) \\
 93464 &:= (((F((9 - 3)) + F(4!)) + (6!)) + F(4!)) \\
 93465 &:= (9 + ((F(3) \times F(4!)) - (-6 \times 5!)) \\
 93466 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F((F(4)!)) + ((F(6)!/F(6)))) \\
 93467 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(F(F(4))) - (-6 - 7!)) \\
 93468 &:= (-9) - ((-F(3)) \times F(4!)) - ((6! + F(8))) \\
 \\
 93470 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 0 \\
 93471 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 1 \\
 93472 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 2 \\
 93473 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 3 \\
 93474 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 4 \\
 93475 &:= 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

- $93476 := 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 6$
 $93477 := 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 7$
 $93478 := 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 8$
 $93479 := 9 \times F(F(F(3!))) - 4 - 7! + 9$
- $93480 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(4))! - ((8 - 0!)!))$
 $93482 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (F((F(4))!) - ((8 - F(2))!)))$
 $93483 := ((9 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(4)))) - ((F(8)/3)!))$
 $93484 := (((-9!) - 3!)/(-4) + F((F(8) - F(4))))$
 $93486 := (9 - ((-F(3)) \times F(4!)) - ((F(8) + 6!)))$
 $93487 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (F((F(4))!) - (F(8) - 7!)))$
 $93490 := ((-F((F(9)/F(3)))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (9 + 0!))$
 $93492 := ((9 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(4)))) - ((9 - 2)!))$
 $93496 := (((F(9) - 3) \times 4) \times (F(9) + 6!))$
 $93498 := -((((9 - F(3))! - 4!) - (9 \times F(F(8))))$
 $93524 := (((F(9) + F((-((F(3) - 5))))!) \times 2) + (((F(4))!)))$
 $93534 := (-(((F(9) + F(3)) - (5^{3!}))) \times (F(4))!)$
 $93536 := ((F(9) + 3) \times ((5! \times F(F(3!))) + F(6)))$
 $93537 := ((9 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (5 + F(3)))) - (7!))$
 $93542 := (((-F(9)) + 3!!) + 5!) - (F(4!) \times (-2))$
 $93543 := (-9) + (F(3) \times (5! + ((F(4))!^{3!})))$
 $93546 := (-((F(9) \times 3!)) + ((5^{F(4)!}) \times 6))$
 $93559 := (F(9) - ((3!! + 5) \times (-5! + 9)))$
 $93564 := (-((F(9) - (3 + (5^6)))) \times (F(4))!)$
 $93565 := (((-9) + (3!^5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5$
 $93566 := -((F(9) - (((F(3) + 5!) + F(6)) \times 6!)))$
 $93568 := (F(9) \times (((F(3))! / 5!) + F(6)) \times 8)$
 $93573 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + ((5! - 7!) - F(F(3!))))$
 $93576 := ((9 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 5)) - (F(F(7)) \times F(F(6))))$
 $93579 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (5 \times F((7 + 9))))$
 $93594 := ((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) + ((5! + 9) \times ((F(4))!)))$
 $93600 := (((-9) \times 3!!) - (F(6))!) \times (-0! + 0!))$
 $93602 := ((((-9) \times 3!!) - (F(6))!) - 0!) \times (-2)$
 $93605 := (((F(9) - F(3!)) \times (-6!)) - 0!) \times (-5)$
 $93608 := (((F(9) + 3!!) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0!) \times 8$

- $93624 := ((((-9) \times 3!!) - (F(6))!) \times (-2)) + (4!))$
 $93632 := ((9! - (((F(3))! / 6!)^3)) / 2)$
 $93634 := ((F(9) + ((3!^6) \times 3)) - F(4!))$
 $93639 := ((((-9) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(6))!) \times F(F(3!))) / 9)$
 $93639 := ((((-9) \times F(F(3!))) + (F(6))!) \times F(F(3!))) / 9)$
 $93642 := (((9 \times 3!!) + F(F(6))) + (F((F(4))!))!) \times 2)$
 $93644 := (((9 \times F((3 + 6)))^{F(F(4))}) + F((F(4))!))$
 $93645 := (((9^{-3+F(6)}) - (F((F(4))!))!) \times 5)$
 $93648 := (((F(9) + 3!) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4))!))! \times 8)$
 $93652 := ((F(9) - F(3!)) \times ((6! \times 5) + 2))$
 $93654 := (((9 \times 3!) + 6!) \times (5! + F(F(F(4))))))$
 $93655 := (((9 + F(F(F(3!)))) + (6^5)) \times 5)$
 $93663 := ((9 \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))))) - ((F(6))! / F(3!))$
 $93664 := (((F(9) + F(3!)) + (6!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F((F(4))!))$
 $93666 := ((-F(9)) + (F(3!) \times F(F(6)))) \times (6! - F(F(6)))$
 $93673 := (((-((9! / F(3))) - F(F(F(6)))) + (7!)) / (-F(3)))$
 $93697 := (F(9) + (((F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9) - (7!)))$
 $93704 := (-F(9)) \times ((F(F(3!)) - F(F(7))) \times F((0! + (F(4))!)))$
 $93707 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (7! - F(F(07))))$
 $93717 := (((-F(9)) \times (F(F(3!)) - F(F(7)))) + 1) \times F(7)$
 $93730 := (((9 + F(F(3))) \times F(7)) \times (3!! + 0!))$
 $93734 := ((9! / F(F(3!))) + (7 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - 4!)))$
 $93744 := (F(F((9 - 3))) \times (7! - (4! \times 4!)))$
 $93746 := (((F(9) \times 3) + F(7)) \times ((F(4))!))! + F(F(F(6)))$
 $93747 := ((9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - ((-F(7)) \times F(F((F(4))!))) + (7!))$
 $93753 := (((F(9) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(7))) \times (5! - F(F(3!))))$
 $93757 := (((-93) \times 7!) / (-5)) + F(7)$
 $93762 := (((9^{-3+7}) + (F(6))!) \times 2)$
 $93764 := (((F(9)^{F(3)}) + 7!) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F((F(4))!)))$
 $93765 := ((-F(9)) + (3 \times F(F(7)))) \times (F(F(6)) + 5!)$
 $93768 := ((9! / F(3)) - ((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8))$
 $93772 := (F(9) \times (((F(F(3!)) - F(F(7))) \times (-F(7))) + 2))$
 $93784 := (F(9) + (3! \times ((F(7) - 8)^{F(4)!})))$
 $93786 := (((-9) \times 3!!) + F((F(7) + 8))) \times F(F(6))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 93828 &:= ((((-9) \times 3!!) + F(F(8))) + 2) \times F(8)) \\
 93834 &:= (((9! - 3!!)/(-8)) - (-3) \times F(4!)) \\
 93840 &:= ((F(9) \times (F(3) + F(8))) \times ((4 + 0!)!)) \\
 93847 &:= (((9 - F(3)) \times 8!)/F(4) - F(F(7))) \\
 93848 &:= ((9!/F(3)) - ((F(F(8)) + F(4)) \times 8)) \\
 93864 &:= (((9!/F(3)) - (F(F(8)) \times F(6))) - F((F(4)!))) \\
 93866 &:= ((9!/F(3)) + ((F(F(8)) \times (-F(6))) - 6)) \\
 93872 &:= ((9!/F(3)) + (F(F(8)) \times (-7 - F(2)))) \\
 93874 &:= (F(9) - ((3!! + (8! \times (-7)))/F(4))) \\
 93879 &:= (9! - ((3^8) \times (7 + F(9)))) \\
 93880 &:= ((9!/F(3)) + (-8) \times (F(F(8)) - 0!)) \\
 93924 &:= (9 \times (-(((F(3)^9) - 2)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 93933 &:= (((F(9) \times 3!) + 9) \times F(F(3!)) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 93940 &:= (F((9 + 3!)) \times (F(9) + ((4 + 0!)!)) \\
 93944 &:= ((9!/F(3)) - ((-9) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \times F((F(4)!))) \\
 93946 &:= (F(9) + (((F(3)!)/(-9)) + F((F(4)!)) \times (-F(F(6)))))) \\
 93954 &:= ((9 - 3) \times (F(9) + (5^{F(4)!}))) \\
 93956 &:= ((F(9) \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(((9 - 5)!)) \times (-6))) \\
 93963 &:= (9 + (((F(3)!)/9) - 6) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 93969 &:= (-9) - ((F(F(F(3!))) - ((9!/6!)) \times (-9)) \\
 93978 &:= (9 \times ((F(3!) \times (-9 \times 7)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 94034 &:= ((F(9)^{F(4)}) - ((0! - 3!) \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\
 94035 &:= (((F(9)^{F(4)}) + 0!) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-5)) \\
 94046 &:= (-F(9)) - (((F((F(4)!)))/((0! + F((F(4)!)))) \times (-F(F(6)))))) \\
 94048 &:= ((9 \times ((F(4)!))!) + (F((F(04)!)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 94059 &:= (((9 - (F((F(4)!))!)) \times F(F((0! + (5)))))/(-9)) \\
 94079 &:= ((-9) + ((F((F(4)!))! \times F((0! + (7)))))/9) \\
 94080 &:= ((9! \times F(F((F(4)!)))/((0! + (80)))) \\
 94083 &:= ((-9) + (((F(4)! + 0!) \times (-8!)))/(-3)) \\
 94088 &:= (((F(9) \times 4!) - 0!) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 94089 &:= (9 - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times ((08)!/(-9)))) \\
 94096 &:= (((F(9) \times 4!) + F(F(-(0! - 9)))) \times F(6)) \\
 94136 &:= (-F(9)) - ((-F(F(4))) \times (F((-1 + F(F(3!)))) + (F(6)!))) \\
 94142 &:= (-F(9)) - (((((4 - 1)!))! + F(4!)) \times (-2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}94144 &:= (-F(9)) - ((-(F(4)!) + 1) - ((F(4)!)!) \times F(F(4))) \\94158 &:= (9 \times ((-4) \times (1 + 5!)) + F(F(8))) \\94168 &:= (((-F(9)) + F((F(F((F(4)!)!)) - 1))) \times F(6)) + 8! \\94204 &:= (F(9) + (((F((F(4)!)!)! + F(20)) \times F(F(4)))) \\94234 &:= ((F(9) + 4!) + (2 \times (3!! + F(4!)))) \\94239 &:= (-9) \times (((F(F((F(4)!)!))² - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(9)) \\94242 &:= (((F(9) + ((F(4)!)!) - (F(2) - F(4!))) \times 2) \\94244 &:= (((F(9) + F(4!)) + (((2 + 4)!)!)) \times F(F(4))) \\94248 &:= ((F(9) \times (F(4)!) \times ((-2) + 4!) \times F(8)) \\94257 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) - ((2 \times 5!) + F(F(7)))) \\94275 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) - ((2 \times F(F(7))) + (5)))) \\94304 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F((F(4)!)!)³ + 0!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) \\94305 &:= ((9!/(F(4)!) - (F((F(F(3!)) - 0!)) \times (-5)) \\94318 &:= ((F(9) + ((F((F(4)!)!)! / 3)) \times (-1 - 8)) \\94324 &:= ((-9) + F((-4) + F(F(3!)))) + (2 \times F(4!)) \\94325 &:= ((9!/4) - ((3!! + F(2)) \times (-5)) \\94332 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) + (-F(F(3)) - F((F(F(3!)) - 2)))) \\94333 &:= (F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) + (F(3) \times F(((F(3) + F(3))!))) \\94334 &:= (F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) + (F(F(3)) + (F(3) \times F(4!)))) \\94336 &:= ((F(9) + (F(F(4)) \times 3!!)) \times (F(3)⁶) \\94338 &:= (9 \times (((F(F(4))^{F(3!)} - 3!!) + F(F(8)))) \\94342 &:= ((9 + F((-4) + F(F(3!)))) + (F(4!) \times 2) \\94344 &:= ((F(9) \times (((F(4)!)! - F(F(3!))) \times 4) - ((F(4)!)!) \\94346 &:= ((9 \times (-F((F(4)!)!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (4⁶) \\94347 &:= (F((F(9)/F(F(4)))) + (F(3) \times (F(4!) + 7)) \\94354 &:= (F(9) + (((F(4)!)!) \times (3! + (5^{F(4)})))) \\94359 &:= (((-9) - (F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times (-((F(3)!)! + 5!)))) / 9 \\94362 &:= ((9⁴) + (F(F(3!)) \times F((F(F(6)) - 2)))) \\94364 &:= ((9 \times (-((F(4)!)! + F(F(F(3!)))))) - (F(6)⁴) \\94367 &:= ((F(9) + F((4! - F(3)))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)) \\94368 &:= (((F(9) \times (4! + F(F(3)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 8) \\94373 &:= ((9 \times ((4! + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(7)))) + F(3!)) \\94374 &:= (9 \times (((4! + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\94376 &:= (((F((9 + 4)) - F(F(3))) \times F(F(7))) + (F(6)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 94384 &:= (F(9) \times ((4! \times F(3!)) + F((F(8) - F(4)))))) \\
 94393 &:= (-(((F(9) - (4))^3)) + F((F(9) - F(3!)))) \\
 94395 &:= ((F(9) - F(4)) \times (F(F(3!)) + ((9!/5!))) \\
 94398 &:= (((-F(9)) + ((F(4))!)) \times (-3!)) + (9 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 94406 &:= ((-F(9)) + (F((F(4))!))!) + ((F((F(4))!) \times F((-0! + F(F(6)))))) \\
 94425 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - ((F(F((F(4))!)^2)))) - 5!) \\
 94427 &:= (((-(9^{F(4)})) - F(4!)) \times (-2)) + F(F(7))) \\
 94431 &:= ((-9) + (F((F(4))!))!) - (-F((F(4))!) \times F((F(F(3!)) - 1))) \\
 94434 &:= (((9 + F(4!)) \times F(F(4))) - ((F(3!))!/(-4!))) \\
 94435 &:= (F((F(9) - 4!)) \times (F((-4) + F(F(3!)))) + 5!) \\
 94437 &:= (9 \times (F((F(4))!) + ((4! + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 94440 &:= ((F((9 - F(4))))! - (-F((F(4))!) \times F((F(F((F(4))!) - 0!)))) \\
 94443 &:= (((F(9)/F(F(4)))^4 - (4!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 94446 &:= (((F(9)/F(F(4)))^4 - F(F((F(4))!))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 94448 &:= ((F(9) + ((-F(4!)) - ((F(4))!)))/(-4)) \times 8 \\
 94462 &:= (-F(9) + (((F((F(4))!))! - ((F((F(4))!) \times F(F(F(6)))))) \times (-2)) \\
 94464 &:= (((F((9 + F(4))) + F(4!)) + (6!)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 94466 &:= (((((9 - 4))! - (4)) \times 6!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 94468 &:= (((9!/F(F(4)) + F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 94473 &:= (((F(9) \times (-4)) + (F((F(4))!))!) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)})) \\
 94474 &:= ((9 - (F(4!)/F(F(4)))) + (7^{F(4)!})) \\
 94477 &:= (((F((9 \times F(F(4)))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 7) - F(F(7))) \\
 94482 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - ((F((F(4))!))!/(8 + 2))) \\
 94484 &:= (((F(9) + F(4!)) \times F(F(4))) + ((8!/4!))) \\
 94487 &:= (-9) + ((4 \times 4) \times (F(F(8)) - (7!))) \\
 94494 &:= (((9!/4!) - 4!) + 9!)/4 \\
 94500 &:= ((9 \times F(F((F(4))!))) \times 500) \\
 94528 &:= ((F((9 \times F(F(4)))) - (5!^2)) \times (-8)) \\
 94546 &:= (((-9!)/((F(4))!))! - ((-5) \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (F(6)!)) \\
 94554 &:= (F(9) \times (F(F((F(4))!)) + ((5! - 5) \times 4!)) \\
 94563 &:= ((-9) + ((F(4))!)) \times ((5! + F(F(6))) - F(3!)) \\
 94566 &:= ((F(9) \times 4!) + ((5^6) \times 6)) \\
 94584 &:= ((9 - F((4 \times 5))) \times (-8 - (F(4))!)) \\
 94605 &:= (((F(9) \times 4!) - F(F(6))) \times (-0! - 5!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 94618 := ((F(9) × F((4! - (6 + 1)))) + 8!)
94624 := (((-F(9)) - ((F(4))!)) × (-F(6)²)) + F(4!)
94626 := ((F(9) × ((F(4) × F(F(6)))²)) - (F(6))!)
94627 := (((9⁴) + 6!) - 2) × F(7)
94634 := ((9 × (4! + F(F(F(6)))))) - (F(3!)⁴)
94642 := ((-((F((9 + 4)) + 6!)) - F(4!)) × (-2))
94643 := ((F(9) + (F((F(4))!))!) + (F(F((F(F(6))/F(4))))^{F(3)}))
94644 := ((-9) - 4!) × ((6! - F(4)) × (-4))
94647 := (((9^{F(4)}) + ((F(6))!/F(4))) × 7)
94648 := ((F(9) × ((4! - 6!) × (-4))) - 8)
94653 := (((9⁴) + 6!) × F((5 + F(3))))
94664 := (((9! × (F(4))!) - F(6))/(F(F(6)) + F(F(4))))
94665 := ((9 × ((F(F((F(4))!)) × (-F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6)))))) + 5!
94673 := ((F(((9 + 4) + 6)) × F(7)) + (F(3))!)
94674 := (((9⁴) + 6!) × F(7)) + F(F((F(4))!))
94677 := (((F(9) × F(F(4))) + (F(6))!) + (F(F(7)) × F(F(7))))
94678 := ((-9) × 4!) - ((F(F(6)) × (-7!)) + F(F(8)))
94683 := ((9⁴) - (((F(6))! - F(F(8))) × (-3)))
94688 := ((9 × F(4!)) + ((F(6) + 8!) × (-8)))
94689 := ((9!/4) + (F(F(6)) × (F(8) × 9)))
94698 := (-9!) + (((F(4!) - 6) × 9) + 8!)
94724 := (((F(9) - (F(4))!) × (7! - F(2))) - F(4!))
94734 := (((-9) × (F(4))!) + (7!)) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(4)))
94739 := (((9 × F(4!)) - F(7)) + (F(3))!) - 9!
94743 := (-9) + (((F((F(4))!))! - (7 × F(4!)))/(-3))
94744 := (F(9) - ((F(F(4)) × (-7)) × F((4! - (4))))))
94746 := (((F(9) - (F(4))!) × 7!) - F(4!)) - 6
94752 := (((-94) × 7!)/(-5)) × F(2)
94753 := (((-94) × 7!)/(-5)) + F(F(3))
94754 := (((-94) × 7!)/(-5)) + F(F(4))
94758 := (-F(9)) × ((F(4))! - ((F(7) + 5!) × F(8)))
94765 := (-9) + ((F(F((F(4))!)) × 7!) - ((F(F(F(6))) + 5!)))
94767 := (((9 + F(4))!)/7!) - (F(F(6)) × F(7))
94768 := ((((-9) + F(4)) + 7!) × F(F(6))) - F(F(8))

- 94773** := $((9!/4) + 7!) - F((F(7) + 3))$
94786 := $((9 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (F(F(7)) \times (8 + F(6))))$
94787 := $((F(9) \times ((F(4))!)) - (-7 + F(F(8)))) \times 7$
94794 := $((F(9) - (F((F(4))!) \times (7!/(-9)))) \times F(F((F(4))!)))$
94807 := $((((9 + F(4))!)/(8 - 0!)) - F(F(7)))$
94824 := $(9 \times ((F(F(4)) - (F(8)^2)) \times (-4!)))$
94831 := $((-F(9) + (F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(8))) \times F(F((3! + 1))))$
94835 := $((9 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + ((-F(8) + 3!) \times 5!))$
94836 := $(((-F(9) + ((F(4))!)) - (-F(8) \times 3!)) \times 6$
94854 := $(((-F(9) - (F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times (-F(8) + (5)))))/F(4))$
94860 := $((-F(9) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (-F(8) \times ((F(6) - 0!))!))$
94864 := $((((9!/F(F(4))) + 8!)/6!)^{F(F(4))})$
94867 := $(((-9) \times F(4) - F(F(8))) + (F(F(6)) \times 7!))$
94869 := $(((-9) \times (4! + F(8))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9$
94873 := $-(((F(F((9 - F(4)))) + F(F(8))) - (7! \times F(F(3!)))))$
94876 := $(((-9) \times F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) + (7! \times F(F(6)))$
94886 := $((((9 - F(F(4))))! \times F(8)) - (F(F(8)) + F(6)))$
94887 := $(((-9) + F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) + (F(8) \times 7!)$
94889 := $((9^{F(4)!}) - (-8 \times 8!))/9$
94894 := $((9!/F(4) - F(F(8))) - (9!/4!))$
94896 := $((F(9) \times 4!) - ((8!/(-9)) \times F(F(6))))$
94904 := $((F(9) + (((F(4))!)) \times (-F(9) - 0!))) \times (-4)$
94928 := $(F(9) - ((F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-((9 - 2)!)) + F(F(8))))$
94937 := $((F(9) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + (9 + (F(F(3!)) \times 7!))$
94944 := $((9 \times F(4!)) - (-F(9) \times F(4!)))/F(F((F(4))!))$
94968 := $(((-9!) + ((F(4) + 9)!)) \times (-F(6)))/(-8!)$
94974 := $(((-9!) + ((F(4) + 9)!)/7!) + (F(4))!$
94978 := $((9 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - ((F(9) \times F(7)) \times 8))$
94986 := $((F(9) \times ((F(4))!)) + (9 - 8!)) \times (-6)$
95036 := $(-9) - ((-5) \times (-0! + F(F(F(3!)))) - (F(6))!)$
95040 := $((9 + F((5 - 0!)))!)/(((F(4))! + 0!))!$
95043 := $((9!/5!) + F(-((0! - 4!))) \times 3$
95045 := $((F((F((9 - 5))!))! - ((-0!) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times (-5))$
95046 := $(-9) - ((-5) \times (0! + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (F(6))!)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 95064 &:= (F(9) \times (((5 + 0!)! - F(F(6))) \times 4)) \\
 95074 &:= (F(9) - (-((5! - 0!) + F(7))) \times ((F(4))!)) \\
 95076 &:= (9 \times ((-5) - F((0! + F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 95084 &:= ((F(9) - (-5) \times F(F(08)))) + (F((F(4))!)) \\
 95184 &:= ((9!/(-5)) + (F(F(-(1 - 8)))) \times ((F(4))!)) \\
 95256 &:= ((F(((9 - 5)!)) \times 2) + (5! \times F(F(6)))) \\
 95304 &:= ((F(9) \times (5^{3! - 0!})) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 95327 &:= (((9!/5) + F((F(F(3!)) + F(2)))) + (7!)) \\
 95337 &:= (9 \times (((5^{3!}) + F(3!)) - (7!))) \\
 95344 &:= (((-F(9)) + (-5) \times (F(3!)!)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) / (-F(F(4))) \\
 95346 &:= (9 \times (((5! \times (-3)) + F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 95347 &:= ((F((9 + 5)) - 3!) \times (4! + F(F(7)))) \\
 95368 &:= (((9 + 5!) + F(3)) \times (6! + 8)) \\
 95404 &:= (F(9) \times ((5! + F(F(4))) \times (-0! - 4!))) \\
 95417 &:= ((9!/(-5)) - (((F(4))! + 1) \times (-F(F(7)))) \\
 95424 &:= (((F(9) \times (5! - F(4))) - 2) \times 4!) \\
 95425 &:= ((F(9) \times (-5!) + ((F(4))!)) + F(25)) \\
 95432 &:= (((-((F(9) - 5!))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(3!)!)) \times 2) \\
 95436 &:= (((-9) - 5!) - F(4)) \times (-3 - 6!) \\
 95445 &:= (9 \times ((-5) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) + ((F((F(4))!))! / (-5!))) \\
 95460 &:= ((9 + 5!) \times (((F(4))! + (F(F(6)) - 0!))) \\
 95463 &:= (9 \times ((-((5! \times F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3!)))) \\
 95464 &:= (((9 + 5!) \times ((F(4))!)) + F((-6) + 4!)) \\
 95469 &:= (((-9!/5!) - F(F((F(4))!))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 9)) \\
 95472 &:= (F(9) \times ((5! \times 4!) - 72)) \\
 95473 &:= (((-9) \times 5!) \times 4!) + F((F(7) \times F(3))) \\
 95475 &:= (-95) \times (F(4) + (7! / (-5))) \\
 95489 &:= (((-9!/5!) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(F(8)) \times 9)) \\
 \\
 95490 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 0 \\
 95491 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 1 \\
 95492 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 2 \\
 95493 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 3 \\
 95494 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 4 \\
 95495 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 95496 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \times 9 + 6 \\
 95497 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \times 9 + 7 \\
 95498 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \times 9 + 8 \\
 95499 &:= -9!/5! + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \times 9 + 9 \\
 \\
 95537 &:= (((F(9) \times (5^5)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(F(7))) \\
 95544 &:= (((F(9) \times 5!) - 5!) + F(F((F(4)!))) \times 4! \\
 95632 &:= (-9!) + ((-5) + F(F(6))) \times F((F(F(3!)) + 2))) \\
 95634 &:= (((F(9) + (5)) + 6!) \times F(F(3!))) \times (F(4)!) \\
 95666 &:= (((F(9) \times 5!) + F(F(F(6)))) + (((F(6)!) + (F(6)!))) \\
 95676 &:= (F(9) \times (((-5!) + F(F(6))) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))) \\
 95726 &:= -((F(9) - ((5! + F(7)) \times F(2)) \times 6!)) \\
 95733 &:= (((9 + 5!) \times F(F(7))) + (3! \times F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 95734 &:= ((-F(9)) - (-((5! + F(7))) \times 3!)) + F((F(4)!)) \\
 95736 &:= (-(((9 - 5)!)) + (-7!) \times (F(3) - F(F(6)))) \\
 95743 &:= (-9) - (((-5!) + F(7)) \times ((F(4)!)!) + F(3!)) \\
 95746 &:= (-((9 + 5)) + (-7!) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(6)))) \\
 95748 &:= (9 - (((-5!) + F(7)) \times ((F(4)!)!) + F(8))) \\
 95749 &:= (-9) - (-((5! + 7)) \times (((F(4)!)!) + F(9))) \\
 95751 &:= (-9) + ((5! + F(7)) \times ((5 + 1)!)) \\
 95754 &:= (((-95) \times 7!) / (-5)) - (F(4)!) \\
 95756 &:= (-((9 - 5)) + ((F(7) + 5!) \times 6!)) \\
 95758 &:= (-F((9 + 5))) \times (-F(F(7)) - F(F((-((5 - 8))!)))) \\
 95760 &:= (((-95) \times 7!) / (-6 + 0!)) \\
 95762 &:= (F(F((9 - 5))) - (-7!) \times (F(F(6)) - 2)) \\
 95763 &:= (9 + (((5! + F(7)) \times 6!) - 3!)) \\
 95764 &:= ((F((9 + 5)) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6)))) + (F(4)!)) \\
 95769 &:= (9 - (-((5! + F(7))) \times (((-6 - 9))!))) \\
 95784 &:= ((F(9) + (5)) \times (7! - F((F(8) - F(4)))) \\
 95788 &:= ((F(9) + 5!) \times ((7!/8) - 8)) \\
 95794 &:= ((F(9) + (-5) \times 7!) + (9!/F(4))) \\
 95828 &:= (-(((F(9) - 5!) \times F((8 \times 2)))) + F(F(8))) \\
 95874 &:= (9 - (((-5) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 95880 &:= ((F(9) \times (5! + F(8))) \times (F(8) - 0!)) \\
 95936 &:= (((9 \times 5!) - F(9)) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

- $$\begin{aligned}
 95966 &:= (- (F(9)) - (- (5) \times ((9! + (F(6))!) / F(F(6))))) \\
 95976 &:= ((9 + 5!) \times (((- (9) + F(7))!) + (6!))) \\
 96057 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(F((0! + (5)))) \times F(7)))) \\
 96066 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F((0! + F(6))) \times F(6)))) \\
 96144 &:= (((F(9) \times 61) \times 4!) + F(4!)) \\
 96174 &:= (9 \times (((F(F(6)) - 1) \times (-F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))) \\
 96193 &:= (F((F(9) - F(6))) - ((1 + F(9)) \times 3!)) \\
 96234 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (2^{F(3!)}))) + (4!)) \\
 96237 &:= (9 \times (((F(F(F(6))) + F(2)) - F(F(3!))) - F(F(7)))) \\
 96246 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((2 \times (F(4))!) \times F(F(6))))) \\
 96256 &:= (((F(9) + 6!) - 2) \times (5! + F(6))) \\
 96264 &:= -(((9! / 6!) \times (F(2) - (F(6) \times 4!))) \\
 96266 &:= (((- (9) + 6!) \times (-((F(2) - (6))))!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 96273 &:= (9 \times (((F(6) \times (-2)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(3!))))) \\
 96306 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(((3 + 0!))!) / (-F(F(6)))) \\
 96325 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(F(F(3!))) - F(2)) / 5)) \\
 96328 &:= (-((9! / F(6))) + (F(3!) \times F((F(2) + F(8))))) \\
 96333 &:= (((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(3!))) - (3 \times 3!)) \\
 96334 &:= ((((- (9!) + (F(6))!) + 3!) / (-3)) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 96336 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (3 \times (3! + 6!))) \\
 96337 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (3!^3))) - F(F(7))) \\
 96338 &:= (((- ((F(9) \times F(6))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(3!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 96346 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(3!) + ((F(4) \times 6!))) \\
 96347 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3! \times F(4)) + 7)) \\
 96348 &:= (- (9!) - (((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(3))) + (4!)) \times F(8))) \\
 96352 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(3) \times 5!)) - 2) \\
 96353 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(3) \times 5!)) - F(F(3))) \\
 96354 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3! \times 5!) \times F(4))) \\
 96363 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3 - 6!) \times (-3))) \\
 96367 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((3 \times 6!) - F(7))) \\
 96379 &:= (F(9) + ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3!) + F(F(7)))) \times 9)) \\
 96384 &:= (((9! / 6!) - F(3)) \times 8) \times 4! \\
 96396 &:= (((- (F((F(9) - F(F(6)))))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 9) - (F(F(6))) \\
 96397 &:= (- (9) - ((F(F(6)) - F(3)) \times (- (F(9) + 7!))) \\
 96408 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(-((0! - 8)))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96414 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(((F(4))! + 1)))) - F(4)) \\ 96423 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(((F(4))! + F(2)))))) + 3! \\ 96426 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + ((4! - (2^{F(6)})))) \\ 96438 &:= ((-F(9)) \times F(F(6))) + (((4!)! \times F(3!)) / (F(8))!) \\ 96442 &:= ((-F((9 + F(6)))) + (F(F((F(4))!))^4) / 2) \\ 96446 &:= (-F(9)) + (((F(F(6)) \times (F(4))!) + F((F(4))!)) \times 6!) \\ 96448 &:= (((F((9 + F(6))) \times F((F(4))!)) - ((F(4))!)!) \times 8) \\ 96450 &:= ((9 + ((F(6))! / F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 50) \\ 96454 &:= ((((-9!) + (F(6))!) / (-F(4))) - 5!) - F(F(F((F(4))!))) \\ 96465 &:= (-((F(9) \times 6!)) - (-F(4) \times ((F(6))! - (5)))) \\ 96467 &:= (-((F(9) \times 6!)) - ((-F(4) \times (F(6))!) + F(7))) \\ 96470 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + (((F(4))! - F(F(7))))) - 0!) \\ 96471 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6)))) - (((F(4))! - F(F(7))) \times (-1))) \\ 96472 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + (((F(4))! - F(F(7))))) + F(2)) \\ 96473 &:= (((F((F(9) - F(F(6)))) + F((F(4))!)) \times F(F(7))) + (F(3))!) \\ 96474 &:= ((-((F(9) \times 6!)) - (F(4))!) + (7! \times 4!)) \\ 96475 &:= -(((F(9) \times 6!) - ((4! \times 7!) - (5)))) \\ \\ 96480 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 0 \\ 96481 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 1 \\ 96482 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 2 \\ 96483 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 3 \\ 96484 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 4 \\ 96485 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 5 \\ 96486 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 6 \\ 96487 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 7 \\ 96488 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 8 \\ 96489 &:= -F(9) \times 6! + F(4) \times 8! + 9 \\ \\ 96496 &:= (((9! / 6!) \times 4!) - F(9)) \times F(6) \\ 96498 &:= (9 \times (-((F(6) - (4! \times (-9)))) + F(F(8)))) \\ 96512 &:= ((F(9) + 6!) \times (5! + F(((1 + 2))!))) \\ 96514 &:= (F(9) + (6! \times (5! + 14))) \\ 96533 &:= (((F(9) + 6!) \times (5! + F(3!))) + F(F(3!))) \\ 96543 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6)))) - (5! \times F(F(4)))) + F(F(3!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96544 &:= (((-9) + F((F(6) + (5))))^{F(F(4))}) + F(4!)) \\
 96594 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F((F(-(5-9))))!)!)/F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 96606 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(F(6))) + (F(F(6)))) - F(F((0! + (6))))) \\
 96614 &:= ((-F(9)) + (F(6) \times F(F(6)))) \times (1 + ((F(4))!)) \\
 96619 &:= (((9!/6) + (F(6))!) - (F(19))) \\
 96624 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (((F(6) - F(2)))!/4!))) \\
 96625 &:= (((9 + F(F(6))) \times 6!) + F(25)) \\
 96626 &:= (((9!/F(6)) + (F(6))!) + F(F((2 + 6)))) \\
 96628 &:= (((9!/F(6)) + (F(6))!) + 2) + F(F(8)) \\
 96634 &:= (((9!/F(6)) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(3))!) + F((F(4))!) \\
 96635 &:= ((9 + F(F(F(6)))) + ((6! - 3!) \times 5!)) \\
 96637 &:= (F((9 + F(6))) + (((6 \times F(3))!)/7!)) \\
 96642 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(6) \times (4! + 2)))) \\
 96644 &:= ((F(9) + (((F(6))!/F(F(6))) + F(4!))) \times F(F(4))) \\
 96645 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(6)) \times F(((F(4))! + (5))))) \\
 96648 &:= (-((9!/6!)) + ((F(6) \times (4))!)/(F(8))!) \\
 96666 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + F(6))) - ((F(6))!/F(F(6)))) \\
 96674 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(6) \times F(F(7))) - (4!))) \\
 96684 &:= ((F(9) \times (6 - 6!)) + (8! \times F(4))) \\
 96696 &:= ((9 + F(6)) \times ((6! - 9) \times F(6))) \\
 96720 &:= (((F(9) \times (-6)) + 7!) \times 20) \\
 96723 &:= (((-F(9)) - F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \times (-F(2) - F(3!)) \\
 96726 &:= (((F(9) - 6!)/(-7)) \times F((2 \times F(6)))) \\
 96728 &:= ((F(9) \times ((6 + 7!)/2)) + F(F(8))) \\
 96734 &:= (((-F(9)) + (F(6))!) + ((7! \times F(3)))) + F(4!) \\
 96744 &:= (((9!)/(F(6) + (7))) \times 4) - 4! \\
 96759 &:= (((96 \times 7!)/5) - 9) \\
 96764 &:= (F(9) \times (-6) + ((7 - 6!) \times (-4))) \\
 96768 &:= (((9! \times F(6))/7!) \times F(6)) \times F(8) \\
 96774 &:= (-9! - (((F(F(F(6))) \times 7) - F(7)) \times (-F(4))!)) \\
 96778 &:= (((F(9) - F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) + (7!))) - 8!) \\
 96782 &:= ((F(F(F((9 - 6))!))) \times 7) + (8!/2) \\
 96794 &:= ((F(9) \times F((6 + F(7)))) + (-9!)/F((F(4))!)) \\
 96813 &:= (((-9) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times (1 + F(3!)) \\
 96824 &:= (((F(9) \times (6! - 8)) - 2) \times 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96831 &:= (-9!) + (F(F(6)) \times ((F(F(8)) \times F(3)) - 1)) \\ 96832 &:= (F(9) \times (((6! - 8) \times F(3)) \times 2)) \\ 96834 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((8!/3!)/4)) \\ 96837 &:= (((9 + 6!) + (8!/3!)) \times F(7)) \\ 96844 &:= (((F(9) \times (6! - 8)) + F(4)) \times 4) \\ 96846 &:= (-9!) + (((F(F(6)) \times F(F(8))) \times F(F(4))) - 6) \\ 96847 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - ((8!/4!) - F(7))) \\ 96849 &:= (((F(9) + F(6)) \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) + 9!)) \\ 96852 &:= (-9!) + ((6 \times F(F(8))) \times (5 + 2)) \\ 96858 &:= (9 \times (((F(6) \times (-8)) - 5!) + F(F(8)))) \\ 96864 &:= (((F(9) \times (6! - 8)) + F(6)) \times 4) \\ 96867 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F((8 + 6)))))) - (7!)) \\ 96873 &:= ((-9!) + F(F(6))) + (F(F(8)) \times (7 \times 3!)) \\ 96894 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - ((F(8) + 9) \times (F(4)!))) \\ 96908 &:= -((F((9 + F(6))) - (9 \times (-0!) + F(F(8)))))) \\ 96913 &:= (F((F(9) - F(6))) + (-F(9) \times (((1 \times 3)!)!)) \\ 96923 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F((F(9)/2)) - 3!)) \\ 96934 &:= ((F((F(9) - F(6))) + (-F(9) \times 3!)) + F(F((F(4)!))) \\ 96936 &:= (((9!/(F(F(6)) + 9)) + F(F(3!))) \times F(6)) \\ 96938 &:= (-((9!/F(6))) + (F((9 - F(3))) \times F(F(8)))) \\ 96944 &:= (-F((9 + F(6)))) + (9 \times (F(4) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\ 96947 &:= ((F(9) - (6! \times F(9))) + F((F(F(4)) \times F(7)))) \\ 96957 &:= ((9^{-6+9}) \times (5! + F(7))) \\ 96967 &:= (((-9) \times 6!) \times (-9 + 6)) - F(F(7)) \\ 96973 &:= ((9 + (F(6))!) + (((F(9) \times 7)^{F(3)})) \\ 96984 &:= ((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(9) \times (F(8) + 4!))) \\ 96996 &:= (((-F(9)) \times F(F(F(6)))) - 9!) + F((9 + F(F(6)))) \\ 97047 &:= (9 \times ((70 + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - F(F(7)))) \\ 97065 &:= ((F(9) - 7) \times (0! - 6!) \times (-5)) \\ 97143 &:= (-9) + (((7 + 1) \times (4)!)/(F(F(3)!))) \\ 97144 &:= (F((F((-9) + F(7))))!) \times (-1 - (-((4)!)/(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\ 97146 &:= (9 \times ((-F((F(7) - 1))) - F((F(4)!)) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\ 97164 &:= (9 \times ((-F((F(7) - 1))) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(4)!)) \\ 97194 &:= (((F(9) \times F(F(7))) - (-((1 - 9)!)) \times (-F(4))) \\ 97236 &:= (9 \times (((7! + 2) \times F(3)) + 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97245 &:= (9 \times (((F(7) + 2) \times ((F(4))!)!) + (5))) \\
 97254 &:= ((F(9) - (7)) \times (2 + (5 \times ((F(4))!)!))) \\
 97264 &:= ((((-9) + F(F(7)))^2) + (6!)) + F(4!)) \\
 97314 &:= (9 - (-(F(7)) \times (F((F(F(3!)) - 1)) + (((F(4))!)!)))) \\
 97323 &:= ((9 \times ((F(7) \times F(3!))^2)) - F(F(3!))) \\
 97327 &:= (((-9!) + (F(F(7)) \times 3!)) / (-2) - F(F(7))) \\
 97335 &:= ((F(9) - (7)) \times ((F(F(3)) + 3!) \times 5)) \\
 97337 &:= ((9 \times ((F(7) \times F(3!))^{F(3)})) - 7) \\
 97338 &:= ((F(9) \times ((7!/3) - 3)) + 8!) \\
 97339 &:= (((-9) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (F(3) + 9)) \\
 97342 &:= ((9 \times ((F(7) \times F(3!))^{F(F(4))})) - 2) \\
 97343 &:= ((9 \times ((F(7) \times F(3!))^{F(F(4))})) - F(F(3))) \\
 97345 &:= ((F((F(9) - F(7))) - F(F(3))) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-5!))) \\
 97346 &:= (F((F(9) - F(7))) - (((F(3) + F(4))!)! \times (-6!))) \\
 97353 &:= (9 \times ((-7) + F(F(F(3!)))) - (5! + F(3))) \\
 97354 &:= ((F((F(9) - F(7))) - (3! \times (-5!))) + F((F(4))!)) \\
 97363 &:= ((-F(9)) - ((-((F(7))!) / (F(3!)!) - (F(6))!)) / F(3)) \\
 97373 &:= (((F(9) \times F(7)) - F(F(3!))) \times F(F(7))) - (3!)) \\
 97376 &:= (F(9) \times (-(((F(7))^3 - 7!) + F(F(6)))) \\
 97388 &:= (((9! - 7!) / 3) - F(F(8))) - F(F(8)) \\
 97389 &:= ((((-9) \times F(7)) - F(3!)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \\
 97398 &:= (-9!) - ((F(7) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-F(9) + 8))) \\
 97406 &:= ((F(9) \times ((7!/F(4)) - 0!)) + (F(6))!) \\
 97424 &:= (((9 - (F(7)^4)) \times (-2)) + (F((F(4))!)!)) \\
 97425 &:= (9 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) - ((F(2) + 5!))) \\
 97432 &:= ((9 \times (-(((7 - F(F(4))))!) + F(F(F(3!)))))) - 2) \\
 97433 &:= ((-9) + ((F(7)^4) \times F(3))) + (F(3!)!) \\
 97434 &:= (9 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) - ((F(3) + F(4))!)) \\
 97435 &:= (((F(9) \times 7!) / F(4)) + (F(3!)!) - (5)) \\
 97437 &:= (-9!) + (((-F(7)) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(7))) \\
 97438 &:= (((F(9) \times 7!) / F(4)) - F(3)) + 8! \\
 \\
 97440 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4))! + 0 \\
 97441 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4))! + 1 \\
 97442 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4))! + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}97443 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 3 \\97444 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 4 \\97445 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 5 \\97446 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 6 \\97447 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 7 \\97448 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 8 \\97449 &:= F(9) \times 7! / F(4) + F(F(4)!)! + 9 \\ \\97452 &:= (9 \times (F((7 \times F(4))) - ((5! - 2)))) \\97454 &:= -(((F(9) \times (F(7) - (4! \times 5!))) + 4!)) \\97455 &:= ((-F(9)) - F(F(7))) \times (-((F(4) \times 5!) + (5))) \\97461 &:= (((-9) \times F(7)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) \times (F(6) + 1) \\97464 &:= (((9! / 7) + F(4!)) - ((6! + 4!))) \\97468 &:= ((F((F(9) - (7))) / F(F(4))) - ((6! + F(8)))) \\97469 &:= (-9) - ((F(7) + (-4) \times 6!) \times F(9)) \\97474 &:= ((F(9) + (((-7) + 4!)! / (F(7)!)) + (F((F(4)!)!))) \\97476 &:= ((F((F(9) - (7))) / F(F(4))) - ((F(7) + 6!))) \\97478 &:= (F(9) \times (-F(7)) + (4! \times ((F(7) - 8)!))) \\97483 &:= ((-9) - 7!) - (F(F(4)) \times (-F(F(8)) - (F(3!)!))) \\97489 &:= (-9!) + (F(7) \times ((F(4!) - F(F(8))) - 9)) \\97493 &:= ((-F(9)) - F((F(7) + F(4)))) + (9 \times F(F(F(3!)))) \\97494 &:= ((9! / 7) + ((F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times (-F(9))) + F(4!))) \\97495 &:= (((-F(9)) \times F(F(7))) + F(4!)) + (9^5) \\97506 &:= (9 \times (((7 - 5!) + 0!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\97524 &:= (9 \times (7! + (F(((5 - F(2)))! / (F(4)!)))) \\97533 &:= (9 \times (((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(F(3!)))) - F(3))) \\97539 &:= (-975) + (F(F(F(3!))) \times 9) \\97542 &:= (9 \times (((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) - F(2))) \\97543 &:= ((9 \times ((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)))) - F(3!)) \\97551 &:= (9 \times ((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))) \\97554 &:= ((9 \times F(F((F(7) - (5)))) - (5! \times F((F(4)!)!))) \\97560 &:= (9 \times (((F(7) - 5!) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0!)) \\97614 &:= -((F(9) \times (F(7) + ((6! + 1) \times (-4)))) \\97626 &:= ((F((9 + F(7))) - (6! \times 2)) \times 6) \\97632 &:= (((F(((9 + F(7)))! + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(3!)!)) - 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97633 &:= (((F(((−(9) + F(7))))!) + F(F(F(6)))) + (F(3!))!) − F(F(3))) \\ 97634 &:= ((F((F(9) − F(7))) + (F(6))!) + F((3! × 4))) \\ 97636 &:= ((F(((−(9) + F(7))))!) + F(F(F(6)))) − (−(F(3)) − (F(6))!)) \\ 97641 &:= ((−(97) + F(F(F(6)))) × (F((F(4))!) + 1)) \\ 97643 &:= (((F(9) × 7) + F(F(6))) × F(((F(4))! + F(3!)))) \\ 97647 &:= (((F((F(9) − F(7))) + (F(6))!) + F(4!)) + F(7)) \\ 97648 &:= (((F(9) + 7!) − (6! × 4!)) × (−8)) \\ 97667 &:= ((9 × (−(((F(7) − F(6))))!) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7))) \\ 97674 &:= ((9 × F((F(7) + F(6)))) + (−(7!)/(F(4)!)) \\ 97677 &:= ((9 × (−(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) − (7!/7)) \\ 97678 &:= ((F(9) × ((F(F(7)) + F(6)) × 7)) + 8!) \\ 97680 &:= ((9 − (F(F(7)) × F(F(6)))) × (−(F(8) − 0!))) \\ 97684 &:= (−(9!) − (F(7) × ((−(6) + F(F(8))) − F(4!))) \\ 97704 &:= (9 × (((−(7) × F(7)) + 0!) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\ 97713 &:= (9 × (−((F(F(7)) − F((F(7) − 1))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\ 97734 &:= (((−(9) + 7!) − F((7 × F(3)))) × F(F((F(4))!)) \\ 97742 &:= (−((F(9) + 7!) − ((7! + F(4!)) × (−2))) \\ 97747 &:= (((F(9) + F((F(7) + (7)))) + ((F(4))!)!) × F(7)) \\ 97749 &:= (−((F(9) − ((7⁷)))) − (F(F(4)) × 9!)) \\ 97774 &:= (−(9) + (7 × ((F(F(7)) × F(F(7))) − (F((F(4))!)!))) \\ 97776 &:= ((97 × 7!)/(F(7) − F(6))) \\ 97777 &:= (((−(F(9)) × F(F(7))) + F(7)) × (−F(7))) − (7!)) \\ 97783 &:= (−((9! − ((7⁷)))) − ((8 + F(F(3))))!) \\ 97784 &:= (F(((−(9) + F(7)))!) − (−((7! + 8)) − F(4!))) \\ 97786 &:= ((9 × F(F(F((−(7) + F(7)))))) − (8 + 6!)) \\ 97794 &:= ((F(F((9 − (7/7)))) × 9) − ((F(4))!)!) \\ 97803 &:= ((9 × (F((F(7) + 8)) + 0!)) − 3!!) \\ 97812 &:= (9 × (−(78) + F(F(F(((1 + 2))!)))) \\ 97833 &:= ((9 × (−(78) + F(F(F(3!)))) + (F(F(3!)))) \\ 97836 &:= ((9 × (7 + F(F(8)))) − (3!! + F(F(6)))) \\ 97837 &:= (((9 + 7!) × F(8)) − (F(3)^{F(7)}) \\ 97839 &:= (((−((9!/7!)) + F(F(8))) − 3) × 9) \\ 97848 &:= ((9 × 7!) − (−(8) × (F(4)⁸))) \\ 97863 &:= ((9 × (7 + F(F(8)))) − (6! − 3!)) \\ 97866 &:= ((9 × ((−(F(7)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(6)))) − (6!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97867 &:= (F(((-9) + F(7)))!) + ((F(F(8)) + (F(6))!) + F(F(7))) \\
 97893 &:= ((9 \times (-F(7)) + F(F(8)))) + (-9!/3!!) \\
 97904 &:= (F((F(9) - (7))) - (9 \times F(F(F((F(04))!)))))) \\
 97913 &:= (F((F(9) - (7))) - (9 \times (-1 + F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 97920 &:= (((-9) + F(7)) \times F(9)) \times (((2 + 0!)!)!) \\
 97924 &:= (((F(9) \times ((F((F(7) - 9)))!)!) + F(2)) \times 4) \\
 97938 &:= (9 \times (-((-((7 - 9))^{3!})) + F(F(8)))) \\
 97944 &:= ((((-9) + F(7)) \times F(9)) \times ((F(4))!)!) + (4!) \\
 97954 &:= (F(9) \times (F(-((7 - 9))) + ((5! \times 4!))) \\
 97958 &:= -(((F(9) \times (F(7) - (F(9) \times 5!))) + 8!)) \\
 97965 &:= (((9 \times F(F(7))) \times 9) + (6!)) \times 5) \\
 97974 &:= (9 \times (-(((F(7) + F(9)) + F(7))) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) \\
 97979 &:= (-9) - (((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) - (7!)) \times (-F(9))) \\
 97979 &:= (-9) - (((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) - (7!)) \times (-F(9))) \\
 97983 &:= ((9 \times (-((F(7) - F(9))) + F(F(8)))) - 3!!) \\
 97988 &:= (F(9) \times ((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) - (8!/8))) \\
 98010 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (0! + F(10)))) \\
 98027 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - (((0! + 2)!)!) + F(F(7))) \\
 98028 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((0! - F((2 + 8)))))) \\
 98034 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((-0!) + F(F(3!))) \times 4!) \\
 98046 &:= (9 \times ((F((8 - 0!)) \times (-4)) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 98047 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - 0!) - (F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 98064 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 0!)) - (F(F(6))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 98082 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 0!)) - ((F(8)^2)) \\
 98136 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - 1) - F((3! + F(6)))) \\
 98138 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + 1) - F((3! + 8))) \\
 98143 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(14) - 3!))) \\
 98145 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 1)) - ((F(4) \times 5!))) \\
 98146 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 1)) - F(((F(4))! + F(6)))) \\
 98153 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (-1 + (5! \times (-3)))) \\
 98154 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (-15) \times 4!) \\
 98174 &:= (-((F(9) - (((8 + 1)!/7))) + F(4!)) \\
 98184 &:= (((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times (1 + 8)) - (4!) \\
 98190 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((1 + F(9)) + 0!))) \\
 98193 &:= ((((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) - 1) \times 9) - 3!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98205 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F((2 + 0!)!))) - 5!) \\ 98227 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F((2 + 2)))!) - F(F(7))) \\ 98234 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((2^{F(3!)} + (4!))) \\ 98235 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(2) - (3! \times (-5)))) \\ 98244 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((2 + 4) + 4!)) \\ 98247 &:= (-F(9)) + ((F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F((F(4)!))) - F(F(7))) \\ 98249 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((2^{F(F(4)!)} + 9)) \\ 98263 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 2)) - F((F(F(6)) - F(3!))) \\ 98264 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - (2^{F(6)})) + (F(4)!)) \\ 98270 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 27)) - 0!) \\ 98273 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - 2) - F(F(7))) - 3! \\ 98274 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(2)) - F(F(7))) - (F(4)!) \\ 98280 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (2 \times F((8 - 0!)))) \\ 98295 &:= (((9 - F(F(8))) + 2) \times (-9)) - 5! \\ 98303 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) - (0! + F(F(3!))) \\ 98304 &:= ((9 \times (8^{3!})) / (04)!) \\ 98306 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((3 + 0!)!)) + F(6)) \\ 98308 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3!))) - 0!)) - 8) \\ 98314 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(3!) \times (1 + 4!))) \\ 98316 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) - (3! + (16)))) \\ 98318 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + ((1 - 8))) \\ 98322 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(3!) \times ((2 + 2)!)) \\ 98326 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + (F(2)^{F(6)})) \\ 98327 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3!))) + F(2))) - 7) \\ 98328 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3!))) - 2)) + (F(8))) \\ 98330 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + (3! - 0!)) \\ 98331 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + ((3 \times 1)!) \\ 98332 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + (3! + F(2))) \\ 98333 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F((3 + 3)))) + F(3!)) \\ 98334 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (((3 + 3)! / 4)) \\ 98335 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!)) - F(F((F(3) + (5)))) \\ 98337 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!)) - (-F(3) + F(F(7))) \\ 98338 &:= (F(9) - (((8^{3!}) \times 3) / (-8))) \\ 98340 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3!)) - ((4 + 0!)!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 98342 := $((-9) + (8! \times F(3))) + F((4! - 2))$
- 98343 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - (3! + F((4 + 3))))$
- 98344 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (3! \times F(4)))) - F((F(4))!))$
- 98345 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + (4 \times 5))$
- 98346 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((-3) + 4!) \times F(6))$
- 98347 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(3))) - (4! \times 7)$
- 98348 := $((F(9) \times F(8)) + (F(3!)!) + ((F(4!) + F(F(8))))$
- 98349 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(3!))) - F((F(4) + 9))$
- 98352 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - (3 \times ((5 - 2)!)))$
- 98353 := $(F((F(9) - 8)) + (-((F(3)^5) \times 3!))$
- 98354 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(3!) \times (5 \times 4)))$
- 98357 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((3!/5) + F(7)))$
- 98358 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (3! \times (5 + F(8))))$
- 98359 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(3))) - (5! + F(9))$
- 98360 := $((9 + (8! \times F(3))) + F((F(F(6)) + 0!))$
- 98361 := $(((-9) + F(F(8))) - F(3!)) \times (F(6) + 1)$
- 98362 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(3!)) - F((6 \times 2))$
- 98364 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (3! - (-6 \times 4!))$
- 98365 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(3!)) - F(F(6)) - 5!$
- 98370 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F((3! + 7) - 0!))$
- 98375 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((3! + F(7)) + 5!))$
- 98380 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3!)) - (80))$
- 98382 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (3! \times (F(8) + F(2))))$
- 98384 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((3! \times F(8)) + (4)))$
- 98385 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(3))) - (8 + 5!))$
- 98387 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (-((3 - 8)!)) - 7$
- 98392 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 3!)) + (F(9) \times (-2)))$
- 98394 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F((3 + 9)) - 4!))$
- 98395 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(3!)) + (9 - 5!))$
- 98397 := $((9!/8)/3! + 9) \times F(7)$
- 98403 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(F(4)))) - (-((0! - 3)!))!)$
- 98406 := $(((-9) + F(F(8))) - F(4)) \times (0! + F(6))$
- 98407 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4 + 0!)!) + F(7))$
- 98408 := $(-F(9)) - ((F(F(8)) - F((F(4))!)) \times (- (0! + 8)))$
- 98409 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) \times (0! + F(9))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
98414 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4! + 1) \times 4)) \\
98416 &:= (-(98) + ((F((F(4)))! + 1) \times F(F(F(6)))))) \\
98418 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(((F(4))! + 1)))) + (F(8))) \\
98421 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F((F(4))!))) - (21)) \\
98422 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) - F((F(4))!)) - 2)) - 2) \\
98423 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(4))) - ((2^{3!})) \\
98426 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! + (2^6))) \\
98430 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 4)) - ((3! - 0!)!)) \\
98431 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4 \times F(F(3!))) - 1)) \\
98434 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(4))!)) - (F(3) + 4!)) \\
98435 &:= ((9 + F(F(8))) + (((F(4))^{3!}) \times 5!)) \\
98440 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F((F(4))!))) - (F(4) - 0!)) \\
98441 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4! \times F(4)) + 1)) \\
98442 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4! \times F(4)) \times F(2))) \\
98443 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4! \times F(4)))) + F(F(3))) \\
98444 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(4))) - ((4! \times F(4)))) \\
98445 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! + 45)) \\
98447 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(4))!)) - ((F(4))! + 7)) \\
98450 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(F(4))^{5+0!})) \\
98452 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((-4) - 5!)/(-2)) \\
98453 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4))!) - F((5 \times F(3)))) \\
98460 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F((4 + 6)) - 0!)) \\
98461 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - ((4!/F(6))!)) + 1) \\
98463 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) + (F(6) \times 3!))) \\
98464 &:= (F(9) \times (((8 - 4) + 6!) \times 4)) \\
98470 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 4)) - (7 + 0!)) \\
98471 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (((F(4))! \times 7) + 1)) \\
98477 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(4))!)) - (F(7) \times 7)) \\
98479 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(4))!) + (-7) - F(9)) \\
98480 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(4))) - (8 - 0!)) \\
98482 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! + F((8 - 2)))) \\
98483 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4 + F(8)) + 3!)) \\
98487 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! + (F(8)/7))) \\
98489 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! - ((8 - 9)))) \\
98489 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! - ((8 - 9))))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98490 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((4 + (9 \times 0)))!) \\
 98493 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4! - (9/3))) \\
 98495 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(4))) + F((F((9 - 5))))!) \\
 98496 &:= (F((-9) + F(8))) \times (-((4 \times 9) + 6!)) \\
 98501 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(((5 + 0!) + 1))) \\
 98502 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((5 + 0!) \times 2)) \\
 98503 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (5 + (03)!)) \\
 98504 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((5 + 0!) + (4))) \\
 98505 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((5 - 0!) + (5))) \\
 98508 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (5 + ((0 \times 8)!)) \\
 \\
 98520 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 0 \\
 98521 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 1 \\
 98522 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 2 \\
 98523 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 3 \\
 98524 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 4 \\
 98525 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 5 \\
 98526 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 6 \\
 98527 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 7 \\
 98528 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 8 \\
 98529 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + (5 - 2)! + 9 \\
 \\
 98530 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 \times 3) + 0!)) \\
 98532 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5!/3!) - 2)) \\
 98534 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5!/F(3))/F(4))) \\
 98535 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + F((5!/(3 \times 5)))) \\
 98536 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 \times 3!) - F(6))) \\
 98538 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5!/(-3 - 8))) \\
 98540 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5^{F(F(4))}) + 0!)) \\
 98542 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5 + 4!) - F(2))) \\
 98543 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5 + (4 \times 3!))) \\
 98544 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (((-5) \times 4!)/(-4))) \\
 98545 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + 5!) - F(((F(4))! + (5)))) \\
 98546 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((5!/F(4)) - F(6))) \\
 98550 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5 - ((5 \times 0)!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98553 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) - ((5 - F(3)))!) \\ 98560 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))) + ((6 \times 0)!) \\ 98567 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5! - 67)) \\ 98568 &:= (9 + ((F(8) + 5!) \times (6! - F(8)))) \\ 98570 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (57 - 0!)) \\ 98574 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5! / F((7 - 4)))) \\ 98578 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5! - ((7 \times 8))) \\ 98594 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + (5! - F(9))) - (F(4)))! \\ 98606 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6))) + (-0! + F(F(6)))) \\ 98607 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6))) + F((0! + (7)))) \\ 98608 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6))) + (0! + F(8))) \\ 98613 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) + ((-1 + 3)!))! \\ 98617 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6! + 1) / 7)) \\ 98625 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (((F(6) + F(2)) - 5!)) \\ 98626 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6 - F(2)))!) - F(6)) \\ 98627 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((6 - F(2)))!) + F(F(7))) \\ 98630 &:= ((9 \times ((F(F(8)) + F(F(6))) - F(3!))) - 0! \\ 98632 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6! / 3!) - 2)) \\ 98633 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6! - 3!) / 3!)) \\ 98634 &:= (F(9) \times (F(8) + ((6! / 3!) \times 4!)) \\ 98635 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((6/3)) + 5!)) \\ 98637 &:= (((9! / F(8)) \times 6) - 3) - 7! \\ \\ 98640 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 0 \\ 98641 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 1 \\ 98642 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 2 \\ 98643 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 3 \\ 98644 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 4 \\ 98645 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 5 \\ 98646 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 6 \\ 98647 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 7 \\ 98648 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 8 \\ 98649 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(6) + F(4)!) + 9 \\ \\ 98653 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(6))) + ((5! - F(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98654 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6!/5) - (4))) \\
 98655 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F((6!/5!)))) + 5!) \\
 98658 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((F(6) + 5!)/8)) \\
 98664 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (6 - (-6) \times 4!)) \\
 98669 &:= (((9! \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) / (F(6)!) - F(9)) \\
 98674 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((F(6) - (7 \times 4!))) \\
 98675 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + 6)) - (F(7) - 5!)) \\
 98679 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - ((F(7) - 9)!)) \\
 98694 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((6 \times F(9)) - 4!)) \\
 98695 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - F((F((9 - 5))))!) \\
 98696 &:= (((F(9) \times 86) \times F(9)) - 6!) \\
 98697 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - (F((-9) + F(7))))!) \\
 98702 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F((7 + 0!)))) - F(2)) \\
 98704 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + F((7 + 0!)))) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 98713 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F((1 + F(3!)))) \\
 98723 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - ((F(2) + 3)!)) \\
 98724 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (7!/24)) \\
 \\
 98730 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 0 \\
 98731 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 1 \\
 98732 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 2 \\
 98733 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 3 \\
 98734 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 4 \\
 98735 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 5 \\
 98736 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 6 \\
 98737 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 7 \\
 98738 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 8 \\
 98739 &:= 9 \times (F(F(8)) + (7 - 3)!) + 9 \\
 \\
 98740 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (F(4)!) - 0!) \\
 98741 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - ((4 - 1)!)) \\
 98743 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (4!/3!)) \\
 98744 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - (F(4)!) + F(4)) \\
 98747 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(((7 - 4)! + (7)))) \\
 98749 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F(-((F(4)! - 9))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98750 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F((5 - 0!))) \\
 98753 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + ((5 - F(3))!)) \\
 98760 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F((F(6) - 0!))) \\
 98767 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((7!/F(F(6))) + F(7))) \\
 98775 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + ((-7) \times F(7)) + 5!)) \\
 98794 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((7!/9)/F(F(4)))) \\
 98802 &:= (9 \times ((F(F(8)) + F((8 + 0!))) - 2)) \\
 98807 &:= (((F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + 0!)) - F(7)) \\
 98814 &:= (((F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + 1)) - (F(4))!) \\
 98820 &:= ((F(9) + F(F(8))) \times (8 + ((2 \times 0)!)) \\
 98829 &:= (((F((9!/8!)) + F(F(8))) + F(2)) \times 9) \\
 98834 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((8!/F(F(3!)))/(F(4)!)) \\
 98835 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}) - 5!)) \\
 98838 &:= (F(9) \times ((8!/F(8)) + F((F(3) \times 8)))) \\
 98843 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((-8) + 4!)/3)) \\
 98844 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F((8 + F(F(4)))) \times (F(4))!)) \\
 98845 &:= (((F((9 + F(8))) - 8!)/F((F(4))!)) - 5!) \\
 98847 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8) + (4! \times F(7)))))) \\
 \\
 98850 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 0 \\
 98851 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 1 \\
 98852 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 2 \\
 98853 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 3 \\
 98854 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 4 \\
 98855 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 5 \\
 98856 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 6 \\
 98857 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 7 \\
 98858 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 8 \\
 98859 &:= 9 \times F(F(8)) + 8!/5! + 9 \\
 \\
 98870 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(8))) + F((F(7) + 0!))) \\
 98874 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + ((8 + 7) \times 4!)) \\
 98875 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + 8) + F(F(7))) + 5! \\
 98883 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) - 8) + F((8 + 3!))) \\
 98884 &:= ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(8) + F(8)))) - F((F(4))!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 98926** := (((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) × 9) - (2 - 6!))
98928 := (((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) × 9) + (-((2 - 8)))!)
98934 := ((((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) × 9) + 3!) + (F(4))!)
98936 := ((((-F(9)) + F(F(8))) × 9) + F(3!)) + (6!))
98937 := (9 × (F(F(8)) + ((F(9) + 3!) + (7))))
98940 := (((F(9) + F(F(8))) × 9) + ((4 + 0!)!))
98964 := (((F(9) + F(F(8))) × 9) - (- (6) × 4!))
98967 := (((9 × F(F(8))) - (F(9) - 6!)) - F(F(7)))
98973 := (9 × (F(F(8)) + (9 - (- (7) × 3!))))
98984 := ((9 × F(F(8))) - ((F(9) - (F(8) × 4!))))
99009 := (9 × (F(F((9 - 0!))) + F((0! + 9))))
99018 := (9 × ((F((9 + 0!)) + 1) + F(F(8))))
99036 := (9 × ((F(9) + ((0! + 3)!) + F(F(F(6))))))
99054 := (9 × (F(F((9 - 0!))) + (5! / F(F(4)))))
99063 := (9 × ((F((9 + 0!)) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3!))
99153 := ((9 × (- (9) + F(F(F((1 + 5)))))) + (3!))
99232 := ((9 × F(F((9 - F(2)))))) + ((3! - 2))
99233 := (((9 × (F(9) + F(2)))^{F(3)}) + F(3!))
99234 := ((9 × F(F((9 - F(2)))))) + ((F(3) + (4))!))
99236 := ((9 × F(F((9 - F(2)))))) + (F(3) + 6!))
99242 := ((9 × ((9²) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) - F(2))
99243 := (9 × ((9²) + F((4! - 3))))
99244 := ((9 × ((9²) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) + F(F(F(4)))
99247 := (((9 × F(F((9 - F(2)))))) + ((F(4))!)!) + F(7))
99264 := ((9 × ((9²) + F(F(F(6)))))) + F(F((F(4))!))
99286 := (F(9) - ((9 × (- (2) - F(F(8)))) - (6!)))
99306 := (9 × ((F((9 + F(3))) - 0!) + F(F(F(6))))))
99314 := ((9 × (9 + F(F(F(3)))))) - (1 - ((F(4))!)!))
99316 := ((9 × (9 + F(F(F(3)))))) - (-1 - 6!))
99324 := ((9 × ((9 + F(F(F(3)))) + F(2))) + (((F(4))!)!))
99333 := (9 × ((93 - F(3)) + F(F(F(3))))))
99336 := ((9 × (9 + F(F(F(3)))))) + (3! + F(F(6))))
99342 := (9 × ((93 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - F(2)))
99343 := ((9 × (93 + F(F(F((F(4))!)))))) - F(3!))
99344 := (((F((9 + 9)) + 3!) + F(4!)) × F(F(4)))

$$\begin{aligned} 99345 &:= (((9 \times (F(9) + F(F(3))))^{F(F(4))}) + 5!) \\ 99347 &:= (9! - (((F(9) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 4!) + F(7))) \\ 99348 &:= ((F(9) + F(9)) \times ((3!! \times F(F(4))) + (F(8)))) \\ 99349 &:= ((9 \times (9 + F(F(F(3!)))))) + (((F(4)!)! + F(9))) \\ 99354 &:= (((9 \times F(F(F((9 - 3)))))) + 5!) + ((F(4)!)!) \\ 99360 &:= (9 \times ((93 + F(F(F(6)))) + 0!)) \\ 99369 &:= ((9!/9) - ((3^{F(6)} \times (-9))) \\ 99384 &:= (9! - (((F(9) - F(F(3))) + F(F(8))) \times 4!)) \\ 99394 &:= ((9! + F(9)) - ((F(F(F(3!))) + F(9)) \times 4!)) \\ 99398 &:= ((F(9) \times (F(9) - F(3!))) + (9 \times F(F(8)))) \\ 99403 &:= ((F(9) + (9^{4+0!})) + (F(3!)!)) \\ 99414 &:= (((F(9) \times (-9)) + (((F(4)!) + 1)!) \times F(F((F(4)!)))) \\ 99423 &:= (9 \times (((F(9) \times F(4)) - F(2)) + F(F(F(3!)))))) \\ 99431 &:= ((9 \times ((F(9) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(3!)))))) - 1 \\ 99433 &:= ((9 \times ((F(9) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(3!)))))) + F(F(3)) \\ 99434 &:= ((9 \times ((F(9) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(3!)))))) + F(F(4)) \\ 99435 &:= ((9 \times (F((9 + F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(3!)))))) + 5! \\ 99437 &:= ((9 \times (9 + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) + (F(F(F(3!)))/F(7))) \\ 99441 &:= (9 \times (((F(9) \times F(4)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 1)) \\ 99449 &:= (((-9!) - (9^{F(4)!})) - ((F(4)!)!)/(-9)) \\ 99465 &:= (-9) + ((9 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((F(6) \times 5!))) \\ 99467 &:= ((-F(9)) + (9 \times F(4!))) - F((F(F(6)) + 7)) \\ 99476 &:= (9 + ((9 \times F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + ((F(F(7)) + (6!)))))) \\ 99477 &:= (9! - ((-9) \times F(((F(4)!) + F(7)))) \times (-7)) \\ 99484 &:= ((F(9) + (9 \times (4! + F(F(8)))))) + ((F(4)!)!) \\ 99486 &:= ((F(9) \times (-9^4)) + (8! \times F(6))) \\ 99504 &:= (9 \times (((-9) + 5!) - 0!) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) \\ 99513 &:= (9 \times (((-9) + 5!) + F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)))))) \\ 99533 &:= (-F(9)) + (9 \times ((5! - 3) + F(F(F(3!)))))) \\ 99534 &:= ((9 \times (((-9) + 5!) + F(F(F(3!)))))) + F(F((F(4)!))) \\ 99542 &:= (-F(9)) - (9 \times (((-5!) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 2)) \\ 99547 &:= (-F(9)) + ((9 \times (5! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))) - F(7)) \\ 99552 &:= ((F(9) \times ((9 - 5)!) \times (5! + 2)) \\ 99558 &:= (9 \times (((-9) + 5!) + (5)) + F(F(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99560 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 \\
 99561 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 \\
 99562 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 \\
 99563 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 \\
 99564 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 \\
 99565 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 \\
 99566 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 \\
 99567 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 \\
 99568 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 \\
 99569 &:= -F(9) + 9 \times (5! + F(F(F(6)))) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 99576 &:= (9 \times (((-9) + 5!) + (7)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 99583 &:= (-9) - ((9 \times (-5!) - F(F(8))) + F(3)) \\
 99584 &:= (-F(9)) - ((9 \times (-5!) - F(F(8))) - (4!)) \\
 99585 &:= (-9) \times (F(F(F((9 - 5)))) - ((F(F(8)) + 5!))) \\
 99594 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F((F((9 - 5))!))) + ((9 - 4)!)) \\
 99603 &:= (9 - (-9) \times (F(F(F(6))) + (-((0! - 3!)!))) \\
 99628 &:= (F(9) - (-9) \times (((6 - F(2))! + F(F(8)))) \\
 99648 &:= (((9 + 9) \times 6!) + F(4!)) + 8! \\
 99649 &:= (((F(9) \times F(9)) - F(F(6))) + (F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times 9)) \\
 99654 &:= ((9 \times ((9 + F(F(F(6)))) + 5!) - F(F((F(4))!))) \\
 99657 &:= (9 \times (F(F(F((9 - 6))!))) + ((5! + (7)))) \\
 99664 &:= (((F(9) \times (F(9) + 6!)) - 6!) \times 4) \\
 99675 &:= (9 \times ((9 + F((F(6) + F(7)))) + 5!)) \\
 99694 &:= ((F(9) \times F(9)) + ((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) + (4!)) \\
 99734 &:= ((9! - (F(9) \times F(7))) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times 4!)) \\
 99744 &:= (((F(9) - 9) - F((F(7) + (F(4))!))) \times (-4!)) \\
 99745 &:= (F(9) - (9 \times ((-F(7)) - F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - 5!)) \\
 99749 &:= ((9! - F((9 + 7))) - (4⁹)) \\
 99774 &:= ((9 \times F((F(9) - F(7)))) + (7!/4)) \\
 99834 &:= ((9 \times (F((-9) + F(8))) + F(F(F(3!)))) + 4! \\
 99844 &:= ((F(9) + (9 \times F(F(8)))) + ((F(4))!⁴)) \\
 99855 &:= (9 \times ((F(9) + F(F(8))) - (5 - 5!)) \\
 99864 &:= (9! - (((F(9) + F(F(8))) - F(F(6))) \times 4!)) \\
 99873 &:= (9 \times ((F((-9) + F(8))) + 7) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 99947 &:= (F((F(9) - 9)) + (F(9) \times (((F(4))!)! + F(7)))) \\
 99963 &:= ((9 \times ((9 \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) + (3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

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